

A Two - Day International Conference on

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

VOL-I

Editors

Dr.M.MAHENDRAPRABU

Dr.G.KALAIYARASAN

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION

ALAGAPPA UNIVERSITY

(A State University Accredited with 'A+' Grade by NAAC (CGPA:3.64) in the third Cycle and Graded as Category -I University by MHRD-UGC)
Karaikudi - 630 003, Tamilnadu, India.

**HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND
MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION**

HOME-2023

A Two-Day International Conference
On

**Holistic Outcome Based and Multicultural Education
(HOME-2023)**

30th & 31st January, 2023

**CONFERENCE MONOGRAPH
(VOLUME -1)**

Editors

**Dr. M. MAHENDRAPRABU
Dr. G. KALAIYARASAN**

**DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
ALAGAPPA UNIVERSITY
(Re-accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC)
Karaikudi**

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ALAGAPPA UNIVERSITY

Alagappapuram, Karaikudi - 630 003, Tamil Nadu, India.

(A State University Established by the Government of Tamil Nadu, Recognised by UGC)
[Accredited with A+ Grade by NAAC (CGPA: 3.64) in the Third Cycle]

Prof. G. Ravi, Ph.D., D.Sc.,
Vice-Chancellor

Message

I am very glad to learn that the Department of Education, Alagappa University, Karaikudi is organizing a Two-day International Conference on *Holistic Outcome Based and Multicultural Education* on 30th and 31st January 2023. This two-day International literary event is organized in keeping with our University's tradition of keeping abreast of all the latest developments in the domain of knowledge. The role played by education, being a social institution serving the needs of society, is indispensable for society to survive and thrive. It should continuously evolve to meet the challenges of the fast changing and unpredictable globalized world. Holistic Outcome Based Multicultural Education is a form of educational practice that focuses on the overall well-being of students and their development of skills within a culturally diverse environment. It acknowledges and celebrates backgrounds and experiences of students. The prime focus of Holistic Outcome Based and Multicultural Education is to help students become engaged member of society and makes them be respectful towards different cultures.

I congratulate the Organizing Secretary and his team of this meet for their earnest efforts and I hope the deliberations of this conference will be fruitful to the academicians, researchers and students. I wish the conference all success.

(G. RAVI)

ALAGAPPA UNIVERSITY

(Established by an Act of the Govt. of Tamil Nadu and recognised by UGC)
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Prof. **S. RAJAMOHAN**, Ph.D.,
Registrar i/c

MESSAGE

I am delighted to know that the Department of Education, Alagappa University Karaikudi is organizing a Two-Day International Conference on "Holistic Outcome Based and Multicultural Education" on 30th and 31st January 2023.

The goal of the conference on Holistic Outcome-Based and Multicultural Education is to foster a more equitable and inclusive education system that is better equipped to meet the needs of all students regardless of their cultural, racial, and socioeconomic backgrounds. The major focus of this conference is to promote culturally responsive teaching approaches, as well as innovative and evidence-based strategies that prioritize outcomes over traditional metrics. Additionally, the conference will explore how to create equitable learning experiences for all students by exploring the intersection of educational policies, technology, and community engagement. By focusing on these topics, the conference seeks to ensure all students have access to the educational opportunities necessary to succeed in today's world.

I hope that the discussions and deliberations during the conference will augment the concept of holistic outcome based and multicultural education to all the participants to make an impact to promote quality education. I wish the Convener, Organizing Secretary, and members of the Conference for their energetic efforts to make this conference a grand success.

I assure that the management will extend all the possible help for such initiatives in the future also.

Wish You Grand Success.

Prof. S. Rajamohan

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অধ্যাপক ড. এস এম হাফিজুর রহমান
শিক্ষা ও গবেষণা ইনস্টিটিউট
ঢাকা বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়
ঢাকা-১০০০, বাংলাদেশ

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It gives me great pleasure to thank the department of education at Alagappa University in Tamil Nadu for organising and hosting this outstanding international conference on holistic education. The abbreviation HOME stands for Outcome-Based and Multicultural Education. Our pals are holding this conference offline due to the pandemic. Offline mode improves both the knowledge and social touches, which were missing during the COVID-19 time frame.

Here, academics from many countries and governments would converge to explore HOME's three key concepts: holistic, outcome-based, and multicultural. Along with academic development, holistic education emphasises the development of the mind, body, and spirit. Education is outcome-based rather than book-based. Education is not just for one race, but for humanity as a whole.

The organisers chose all three ideas appropriately for discussion during the global conference. This conference would have served as a platform for the presentation of numerous ideas and the sharing of information. I am

I'm confident that seminar attendees will gain something from it and strive to implement new ideas in their profession.

I want to thank you for including me in this seminar.

Prof. Dr. J.R. JAWAHARLAL, M.Sc., M.A., M.Ed., M.Phil., Ph.D.
Founder Principal, Bright Riders School, Al Gharbia,
Abu Dhabi, UAE
Director & Academic Advisor,
Love Dale Residential School,
Attingal, Thiruvananthapuram,
Kerala.
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18th January 2023

MESSAGE

Greetings!

The year 2023 is very special to us since the conference provides us with the opportunity to identify the Theme, Impact and Vision for the Zen generation. It is technology that rules us rather than we do. Our future vision is to create even greater value to all corners of the globe. This conference will be one for us to share our thoughts and exchange ideas on how to chart our journey forward to reach new heights. This conference will allow all the scholars to reflect upon and celebrate our past accomplishments, renew our friendships globally, and extend our networks irrespective of caste, creed culture and religion. Hence, we jointly explore current and future research directions in widening the holistic outcome based and multicultural education. We hope that we will have a productive and fun-filled time at this very special conference. To put a conference of this magnitude together is a herculean task. To that end, I want to thank all the Professors for providing their wisdom and guidance; for their tireless efforts to organize all sessions and tracks; for their many contributions including organizing the conference; and for their careful scheduling of events. I would like to thank the Vice-Chancellor of Alagappa University, Karaikudi for providing his generous academic support. Finally, I conclude thanking all the conference participants for their contributions which are the foundation of this conference. I wish the conference every success. Jai hind!

(Dr. J.R. Jawaharlal)

**DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
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Prof.G.KALAIYARASAN
Professor & Head

Message

Gandhiji says “Education means an all round drawing out of the best to the child and man-body, mind and spirit”. Accordingly, Education must help the learners to get a harmonious development. A diverse county like India needs the holistic based and multicultural education in order to cultivate equity, secularism, democracy, fraternity among the child and people irrespective of caste, creed, race, ethnicity, language religion, class and gender. Education should incorporate the history, values, beliefs and perspectives of people from different cultural background so that understanding and appreciation of others beliefs will be developed among the public through education. Therefore, this conference would provide a platform to the delegates to present the paper and to discuss about their views and ideas in implementing the holistic and cultural based education.

I wish the organizers for taken up such a very important title for the International Conference. I wish for a great success.

G. Kalaiyarasan 22/11/23

Dr. G. KALAIYARASAN
Professor & Head
Dept. of Education
Alagappa University
Karaiikudi - 630 003

Dr.M.MAHENDRAPRABU,
Assistant Professor,

ORGANIZER MESSAGE

Education is a crucial component of any nation's progress and development, and the quality of education imparted to its citizens can often be the deciding factor of a country's success. In today's fast-paced, ever-changing world, it is more important than ever for educational systems to reflect the needs of the people and the demands of the times. Holistic outcome-based and multicultural education is a response to this need, and it is becoming increasingly popular in classrooms around the world.

Holistic outcome-based education is an approach that focuses on the development of the whole student. It is an approach that values the individual, and seeks to foster skill development and personal growth through an understanding of the student's individual background and needs. This approach recognizes that students have different learning styles and needs, and strives to meet those needs through a variety of methods and techniques. In short, holistic outcome-based education is an approach to learning that is tailored to the individual student and their unique learning style.

Multicultural education is an approach to learning that acknowledges and celebrates the diversity of cultures, backgrounds and perspectives that exist within a classroom. It is an approach that seeks to understand and appreciate these differences, and to use them to foster an inclusive and open learning environment. Multicultural education seeks to provide students with an understanding of the diversity of cultures, and to promote respect and acceptance of these differences.

Together, holistic outcome based and multicultural education creates an environment in which learning is tailored to the individual and appreciates the diversity of perspectives within the classroom. It is an approach to learning that is both practical and progressive, and one that is becoming increasingly popular in classrooms around the world. This conference aims to explore the successes and challenges of this approach, and to identify strategies for making the most of the opportunities that it provides.

I would like to place on record my words of thanks and appreciation for all the authors of the papers we received. I am extremely grateful to the honorable **Vice-Chancellor Prof.G. Ravi** for having permitted Alagappa University, Department of Education to organize a Two days International Conference on Holistic Outcome based and Multicultural Education (HOME- 2023). I profoundly thank the honorable Vice-Chancellor for his personal guidance and encouragement, rendered for the success of the program.

The role of the **Registrar, Prof. S. Rajamohan** in making this endeavor a grant success, is a commendable one. We bear in our hearts the troubles we undertook for the sake of people like us. I register my sincere thanks for him.

I wish all the Delegates, Special Invitees and Experts a pleasant time during short stay with our **University Officials, Faculty Members, Research Scholars, and Students** of Alagappa University Department of Education.

Dr.M.MAHENDRAPRABU

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Mahendraprabu', with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Organizing Secretary

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

A PILOT STUDY; A RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF THE LIFE ATTITUDE PROFILE-REVISED (LAP-R) FOR MASTER STUDENTS

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Abstract

This paper is a report a reliability and validity of LAP-R scale to measure attitude towards life of master students. A person's attitude towards life will affect a person's lifestyle, economy, social status, and life activities. Therefore, the means of measuring attitude towards life should be sensitive to the purpose, meaning and essence of the person's life. A sample of 114 students of social science SPU completed a structured questionnaire including demographic characteristics and the Life Attitude Profile-Revised Scale in 2022. It was used design test-retest with interval 2 months. Reliability of Pearson coefficient from 52 students and Cronbach's alpha, KMO and Bartlett's test, principal components analysis, internal consistency reliability and were used to measure the psychometric properties of the items of the scale from 114 students. Pearson coefficient range from 0.523 to 0.772 of sub dimension and general coefficient 0.727, Cronbach's Alpha test was .709, retest was .873. KMO from .490 to .680 of all subdimension, Bartlett's test was all significance appropriate .000 ($p < 0.05$). it was counted each sub dimension communalities of principal component Analysis. This LAP-R scale can be used in research to determine students' attitudes towards life from the large groups.

Keywords: *Attitude Toward Life, Master Students, Purpose, Coherence, Responsibleness, Death Acceptance*

Introduction

Students and young people will be the main social, economic and political components of the future, so it is common to study their attitude towards things. It is believed that the way they look at their lives, their future planning, and their search for and definition of the meaning of life has an important impact on deciding who they will become and how they will contribute to society. Therefore, it is appropriate to measure their attitude towards life with a proven psychological scale, and this study aims to determine how appropriate this scale is to be used by students who are growing up under the influence of Indian society and culture and who are keeping pace with global education.

The LAP-R scale, developed by T. Reker, is a scale that comprehensively examines the attitude towards life, including goals, goal-seeking, coherence, choice and responsibility, attitudes towards death, and existential issues. The logotherapeutic constructs of will to meaning, existential vacuum, personal choice and responsibleness, realities and potentialities, and death transcendence comprise the building blocks of Frankl's theoretical structure. (1992 by Gary T. Reker). This scale was developed based on the logotherapy theory of Viktor Frankl, a great thinker of the 20th century. The original version was developed by E. J. Peacock and Gary T. Reker, second version by Paul T. P. Wong, Peacock and Gary T. Reker, and this Life Attitude Profile-Revised version was developed by Gary T. Reker.

The Life Attitude Profile – Revised (LAP-R)

The LAP-R is a 48-item self-report multidimensional measure of discovered meaning and purpose in life and the motivation to find meaning and purpose in life. It is the product of a number of refinements based on a combination of theoretical, rational, and factor analytic procedures (1992 by Gary T. Reker). Each item on the LAP-R is rated on a 7-point Likert scale of agreement (1- 7), ranging from "strongly agree" (7) to "strongly disagree" (1). The LAP-R is scored and profiled in terms of six dimensions and two composite scales (1992 by Gary T. Reker). The six dimensions are (as defined by Reker, 1992): 1. Purpose (PU); refers to having life goals, having a mission in life, having a sense of direction from the past, in the present, and toward the future. 2. Coherence (CO); refers to having a logically integrated and consistent analytical and intuitive understanding of self, others, and life in general. 3. Choice/Responsibleness (CR); refers to the perception of freedom to make all life choices, the exercise of personal responsibility, personal decision making, and internal control of life events. 4. Death Acceptance (DA); refers to the absence of fear and anxiety about death and the acceptance of death as a natural aspect of life. 5. Existential Vacuum (EV); refers to having a lack of meaning in life, lack of goals, lack of direction, boredom, apathy, or feelings of indifference. 6. Goal Seeking (GS);

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refers to the desire to get away from the routine of life, to search for new and different experiences, to welcome new challenges, to be on the move, and an eagerness to get more out of life.

Aim: Aim of this study is to measure reliability and validity of test the LAP-R scale for Gujarat master students.

Design: First step is translating into Gujarati. After, check translating, Researchers collected data from master students of Psychology subjects. It was calculated validity and reliability (Cronbach's alpha) from 114 respondents. It was used method of test-retest. After test-retest was calculated Pearson correlation coefficient of reliability was calculated from 52 respondents who participated 2 times interval 2 months. (Time 1- 12.10.2022, time 2 -11.12.2022)

Data collection: The researchers studying and working in SPU and conducted with the master students. The questionnaire was explained to the students, who then read it and marked their answers on the sheets. The questionnaire took approximately 15-20 minutes to complete. It was given to students in a classroom. 114 of 120 participants completed the questionnaire. Test-retest of the scale was conducted after 8 weeks from 60 students and it was calculated 52 respondents who are completed.

Methods: Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated from excel in Pearson formula. In SPSS, Factor analyses; KMO and Barlett's test, principal components analysis; varimax rotation, internal consistency reliability and Cronbach's alpha were used to measure the psychometric properties of the items of the scale.

Participant Demographics

Table 1

Statistics							
		Gender		Area		Family Type	
N	Valid	110		99		109	
	Missing	4		15		5	
		Male	Female	Urban	Rural	Joint Family	Nuclear Family
Frequency		40	70	45	54	80	29
Percent		35.1	61.4	39.5	47.5	70.2	25.4
Valid percent		36.4	63.6	45.5	54.5	73.4	26.6

The age of the participants is 19-50, 4 participants are 25-50 years old, the rest are 19-25 year old students, most of them are 21 (Frequency-39, Percent-34.2, Valid percent 34.8) and 22 (Frequency-42, Percent-36.8, Valid percent 37.5) years old.

Reliability of Test-Retest

The LAP-R Scale was found to have an overall Pearson's correlation coefficient r of 0.717. Therefore, overall LAP-R scale is high, Pearson's correlation coefficient of the subdimensions ranged from 0.523 to 0.772. Pearson's correlation coefficient's positive and strong value is greater than 0.5 (Turney, S. 2022), Subdimensions were found that Purpose is high, Coherence, Choice/Responsibility, Death Acceptance, Existential Vacuum and Goal Seeking are moderate. (See the table 2)

Reliability/internal Consistency of Cronbach's Alpha

The LAP-R scale was found to have an overall coefficient Cronbach's Alpha of .843. The subdimensions ranged from .577 to .754. The overall coefficient Cronbach's Alpha is high internal consistency, but, subdimensions; Death Acceptance is Acceptable (.754), Purpose (.683), Coherence (.667) and Choice/Responsibility (.685) are questionable, Existential Vacuum (.597) and Goal Seeking (.577) are poor, unacceptable. (See the table 2)

Construct Validity

The overall LAP-R scale calculated KMO was .437 with a P value .000. And subdimensions' KMO ranged from .602 to .770 with P values .000. (See the table 3). Even overall KMO inadequate, subdimensions are indicating that the sample was large enough to perform a satisfactory factor analysis. But, It was checked communalities of principal component analysis 2 versions. One of them was calculated by each subdimensions and it was found to have communalities of acceptable greater than 0.5 except questions pu_26 (Future direction); co_12 (Consuming purpose), 35 (Unified life pattern), 46 (Sense of order/coherence); cr_3

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(Opportunity to direct life), 19 (Freedom to choose); da_25 (Neither fear nor welcome); ev_9 (Lack of meaning), 13 (Lost interest); and gs_10 (New/different things appeal), Maybe we can accept questions; pu_26, cr_3, ev_13, gs_10. (See table 4). Second version was calculated by all 48 items of LAP-R scale and it was found to have communalities of acceptable, ranged from .623 to .909. (See table 5). There is no unacceptable communalities, it is indicating that these questions can be considered to be able to describe the Gujarati students' Attitude toward life and enough to do factor analysis. It was calculated in varimax rotation of principal component analysis. The following criteria were used: eigenvalues higher than 1.0, factor loadings higher than 0.40. Factor loadings of two (co_12, 35) items were inadequate, and these items were removed from the scale. It was extracted 17 factors from rotation sums of squared loadings and cumulative values ranged from 44.540 to 66.417. (See table 7). Cumulated value is accepted. Purpose was extracted three components of factor from 8 items and cumulative value is 62.953, Coherence was extracted two components of factor from 6 items and cumulative value is 44.540, Choice/Responsibility was extracted three components of factor from 8 items and cumulative value is 60.091, Death acceptance was extracted three components of factor from 8 items and cumulative value is 62.953, Existential vacuum was extracted three components of factor from 8 items and cumulative value is 55.896, Goal seeking was extracted three components of factor from 8 items and cumulative value is 57.592. Although, Cronbach's Alpha was unaccepted two dimensions (existential vacuum and goal seeking), Pearson's correlation coefficient was relation of strong positive by test-retest, therefore, it wasn't removed any dimensions when it factor analyzing.

Discussion

The results of this study showed that the LAP-R scale to able to explain attitude toward life of students group. But some results of Gujarat version of the LAP-R Scale indicated that it will need to check its translation and content of some questions. The overall and range of subdimensions' Pearson correlation coefficient of the LAP-R Scale seemed to be sufficient. Internal consistency of overall and subdimensions except two dimensions (existential vacuum and goal seeking) had acceptable. If the value of Cronbach Alpha is within the range of 0.60 to 0.80, it means that the value of Cronbach Alpha is moderate and acceptable. (Daud, K.A.M., Khidzir, N.Z., Ismail, A.R. and Abdullah, F.A. 2018). In the present study, Cronbach's alphas were .667-.754 for the four dimensions (purpose, coherence, choice/responsibility and death acceptance). Factor analysis with varimax rotation indicated that, with regard to the content, six factors could be discerned: purpose, coherence, choice/ responsibility, goal seeking, death acceptance and existential vacuum dimension. Communalities is acceptable this LAP-R scale can explain this student's group's attitude toward life. Also, some questions do not exceed 50% of the representation of the group, so cultural and semantic improvements can be made or removed in the translation. Reker (1992) found that Cronbach's alpha reliability scores of the scales were 0.91, 0.81 and 0.89 respectively in a study with young-aged adults.

Conclusion

This LAP-R scale is suitable for master students for further research. LAP-R scale and subdimensions can explain Gujarat master student's group. However, the translation of scales of subdimensions other than the death acceptance could be improved in terms of cultural understanding. Some questions may not be acceptable for cultural reasons.

Reference

- [1] Anja Mehnert., Uwe Koch. (2008). Psychometric evaluation of the German version of the Life Attitude Profile-Revised (LAP-R) in prostate cancer patients. Published online by Cambridge University Press: Retrieved from. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/>
- [2] Daud, K.A.M., Khidzir, N.Z., Ismail, A.R. and Abdullah, F.A. (2018), "Validity and reliability of instrument to measure social media skills among small and medium entrepreneurs at Pengkalan Datu River", *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 1026-1037.
- [3] ERCI B. (2008) Meaning in life for patients with cancer: validation of the Life Attitude Profile-Revised Scale. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 62(6), 704- 711 doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2008.04658.x
- [4] Reker, G. T. (1992). *Manual of the Life Attitude Profile-Revised (LAP-R)*.
- [5] Trent University, Peterborough, on: Student Psychologists Press.

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Abstract

India is a developing society the social system of India is dominated by domestics, marriages, values, customs and traditions. During the Muslim period, Muslim women were veiled and girls from Hindu families were not allowed to come out of the house because of their brothers. It was done with the intention that when the development of women education is well awaited, surely it will be able to come out of the obstacle and reach its goals.

Key word: *Changes in Gender and Education, The status of women, changes in women Education.*

Introduction

India is a developing society. The social system of India is dominated by caste joint family organization, marriages, values, customs and traditions. From ancient times the patriarchal and patriarchal values have been present in the Indian social system. Her journey through the Middle Ages, which pushed women from inequality to inequality during the Middle Ages, is becoming the seed of current problems. Instead of being an independent identification, Indian women's identification is in the tradition of marriage, family, caste, class, community values and customs. Efforts to improve the status of Indian women since the 19th century have significantly improved the status of women. But for the most part, the situation for women has remained the same. According to the indicator numbers for the status of women, when it comes to the status of women, the status of women in India is considered lower than other countries. The situation of women in India is not satisfactory. An Indian woman lives a life between two realities, one a legal reality and the other a social reality. Education is essential for women to get ahead. It is very important for women to be educated. The status of women in India has been given a high place in the society since the beginning of education. Women have been given priority over men. Ram Sita is called Syam Radha Nahi Sitaram Radhe Syam. Even in various festivals, women are said to be more important in human beings because our radiance is on the left side of the body so any religious act in a man becomes an imperfect human in social and religious functions. The Vedic age was a golden age in Hindu society. In this age women were not only good but very progressive. Opinions from Vedic literature It is known that at that time women had the same status as men in education, marriage, socially, politically and economically. Women had the right to participate jointly with men in education, rites, disputes, etc.

In the Vedic period, women's education, primary education was known in families, while the system of higher education was in ashrams and gurukula. Primary education was imparted to educated children only in educated families. Normally they could not go to Gurukuls and Ashrams for higher education. Even after getting the right to education, there was no system of women's education due to which women's education could not be developed. In the last phase of the Vedic period, the age of marriage for girls was reduced and the barriers to her education were raised. Later, Mahatma Buddha gave new life to the education of women by admitting them to the Sangh. This right was given only to women belonging to elite and inherited classes so education of women of this class was promoted while ordinary women were deprived of education. The centers of learning in the Buddhist period were Madho and Vihar. These centers of learning at both primary and higher levels were established near public settlements. Boys and girls of all castes had the right to enter this educational institution. Hostels for girls were also built in certain monasteries and viharas. After defeating Prithviraj Chauhan, Muhammad Ghori laid the foundation of the Muslim Empire of India in 1192. Women were veiled and girls from Hindu families did not come out of the house due to fear. The spread of female education began to decline. Also took interest in broadcasting.

During the Muslim period, the practice of veil and child marriage was prevalent among both Hindus and Muslims, depriving the entire women's group of the benefits of the session except for the financier girls. The middle-class girls, along with the boys, are the primary sixes in the saloons, and some of them had knowledge of the religious literature. Among the Hindu widows like Raiya Sultan, Gulbadal Begum, Abunisha, Chand Sultan, etc., the names of RaniRupmati, Rani Durgavati, Sask Rani Ahalyabai of Indore and mother Jijabai of Sivji are still remembered by Mahila Siksahan Shektrev. During East India ruling , women's education was conducted by IST India Company in Bengal, Bihar and Magadha provinces of India. Christian Miss Reverend The first separate year for Indian girls was established in Chinsur in 1818. David Hammer also opened a girls school in Calcutta in 1820. David Haber also opened a girls school in Calcutta in 1820. Miss Cook came to India from England in 1821 and re-established 8 girls schools. In 1823 14 girls schools were established in the field of women's education. Many Indians who were influenced by this practice also came forward. Mahatma Phule opened a girls school. In 1849, viceroxy opened a women's school in Calcutta.

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After the first independent struggle against the British in India in 1857, the British government improved primary education. It was natural for the spread of education and to accelerate the field of women's education. 30 years later in 1902 there were 6107 girls sexually abusive institutions with 5628 primary 467 secondary and 12 colleges. Madavi was. The establishment of All India Women's Organization and political awareness also contributed to the development of women

Although the Radhakrishna Commission was formed in 1984 after receiving information with the intention of making suggestions for the improvement of the Indian education system. Appropriate curriculum should be prepared as per their wishes and their proper arrangement educational and vocational guidance for girls was done well as an operational plan to spread women's education in independent India. The process of improving it has also got better with the publicity. The Eleventh Five Year Plan 2007-12 which is currently coming up with a focus on education at all levels for the underprivileged girls. At this level new Navodai schools have also been opened in such districts is coming. In the end, it can be said that the education of well-educated women in ancient times is not a new thing in India. However, it has been awakened in modern times. India could not have developed properly without women's education so many important instructions were given for various education commissions and development from time to time. These suggestions were also implemented gradually. But when the development of women education is well awaited, surely she has been able to break through the barriers and reach her goals.

Conclusion

Education is the basis of progress No society can progress by being uneducated. Today's educated woman knows the importance of both time and education. Today women are playing an active role in every field. Education through education man was kept away from so many the field but today women have also entered the field of advocacy. With the attainment of education, the woman's faith has increased and she is able to solve any problem Will be able to create. Today education has made women aware of their rights and has played a major role in the progress of the society and the country.

References

- [1] Dr. Rajkumar : Indian Women's Social Studies Arjun Publications 2012
- [2] Dr. Manjulata Chillar : Indian Nari Shosan Ke Badleme Ayam
- [3] Dr. Alok Kumar Kasyap : The direction of women in Indian understanding

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THE CURRENT PREDICAMENT OF EDUCATION IN INDIA'S URBAN AREAS

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Abstract

Major world's population is now a day moving towards urban regions. Since the majority of people in a country is moving in urban regions, improving their living conditions is essential to the country's overall progress. To put it simply, education is crucial to a country's progress. As a result, the Government of India has prioritised enhancing the quality of education in light of its significance for the country's growth. Nonetheless, the education system in urban regions continues to face several difficulties. Considering the vital role that urban education plays in India's overall progress, this study aims to shed light on the sector's current state and the challenges it faces. In addition to that, however, the purpose of the report is to make some suggestions in order to improve the quality of urban education in India.

Keywords: *Education, Urban Education, Scenario, Problems, Suggestions*

Introduction

The majority of the world's population may be found residing in urban settings. In India, urban areas are home to around 42% of the country's population. The contribution of urban regions to the growth of the national economy is relatively big, especially in nations that are still in the process of growing, a significant proportion of economic activity is dependent on urban areas. As a result, the entire economic success of many developing nations, including India, depends heavily on the progress made in urban areas. When trying to determine a country's degree of development, education system of that country can be the most significant component to look at. As a result, all aspects of the country's educational system need to be strengthened in order to support the nation's goal of sustained economic growth. Since it is common knowledge that approx. half of India's population lives in urban areas, it stands to reason that the educational system in India's urban areas makes a significant contribution to the overall growth and development of the nation. Education plays a vital part in development of urban family, person, community & society that ultimately leads at a reduction in the amount of poverty that exists and a control over the amount of unemployment that occurs. Education plays a significant part in urban systems of supply, manufacturing, and marketing, as well as in health care, education, staff upkeep, and governance, all of which eventually contribute to the development of urban areas. Education plays an important element too in the process of bringing about societal transformation, increasing the socioeconomic position of people and standard of life, supplying skilled personnel in urban regions, integrating urban and rural sectors, and offering work and income prospects to the people who live in urban areas. Looking at importance of education in metropolitan regions, the government of India has begun a number of initiatives to enhance the educational opportunities available in urban India. Despite these efforts, a significant divide remains between the educational opportunities available in rural and urban areas.

Objectives of the Study

The following is a list of the primary goals that this study aims to accomplish:

- 1) To do research into the current state of schooling in India's urban areas.
- 2) In order to do study into the difficulties those are experienced by urban education in India.
- 3) To make some suggestions for potential improvements to the educational opportunities available in India's urban areas.

Methodology of the Study

This inquiry will mostly concentrate on secondary data that is material, which has been collected from previously published works such as books, papers, journals, and articles that may be accessed online, the major investigation focus at secondary data.

Discussion

There is still a large gap between both the urban & rural educational system in spite of the truth of Right to Education a most fundamental right of every citizen in India. Even if the standard of education in India's metropolitan regions is already pretty high, it is continuing to rise to a higher level. There are many schools in urban areas, but children have to travel a great distance to get an education at better school. As a result, children face many challenges in their attempts to do so. Even while the number of children attending elementary school in urban areas of India is rising, the quality of education at affordable fees in these areas is extremely lacking. Cheap Education in India's urban communities remains one of the country's most pressing

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challenges. The educational system in these areas is afflicted by a number of issues, some of which include a lack of suitable academic institutions and infrastructural facilities, an absence of financial support, & a fairly low level of educator quality due to a shortage of excellent teachers, among many other issues. Moreover, there is a shortage of good teachers, which contributes to the fairly low level of instructor quality. In addition, the majority of families living in urban areas of India are classified as having lower incomes, and as a result, they struggle to provide for their families. They have a poor income against high expense of cities, thus it is difficult for them to achieve their fundamental requirements, which are to have a house, clothing, and shelter. Therefore, in order to satisfy their fundamental wants and requirements and to earn their daily bread, a great number of youngsters who live in urban regions work hard for their earnings. This leads to failure, and they drop out of school shortly after finishing their elementary education.

A Quick Look at the Current State of Affairs in Indian Education Sector

In accordance to the “Annual Status of Education Report 2018”, the following are some of the recent developments that have taken place in India's education sector: In urban India, 97.2% of children between the ages of 6 and 14 are now enrolled in some form of educational programme. In addition to this, the percentage of children aged 6 to 14 who are not enrolled in schools has reached a record low of 2.8% in 2018, marking the first time it has dropped below the 3% mark. These students are split between public schools (69.1%) & private schools (30.9%), with the majority attending public institutions. 4.1% of females in the age range of 11 to 14 are not enrolled in any kind of educational programme. The proportion of students aged 6 to 14 that attend private schools has been relatively stable over the past few years, with enrolment rates of 30.6% in 2016 and 30.9% in 2018. The percentage of pupils who are enrolled in fifth grade and have the ability to read a text at the level of second grade has grown going from 47.9% in the year 2016 to 50.3% in the year 2018. This shows that even after five years of schooling, Despite 3 years, a significant portion of the student population has not even reached the minimum standard that was set for them. This is the case even if they have been in school for the whole five years. The percentage of children in The percentage of people in India who really are competent to do divisions has marginally improved from 26% throughout 2016 through 27.8% in 2018. The percentage of school-aged Indian children who are capable of doing subtraction operations has increased somewhat from 27.6% throughout 2016 through 28.1% in 2018, but is still basically the same. In a similar vein, the percentage of youngsters in India who really are proficient to perform subtraction has increased from 27.6% throughout 2016 through 28.1% in 2018, representing a generally stable increase over time. There has been no discernible shift in the attendance rates of either students or teachers across India as a whole. Over the course of the last several years, elementary and upper primary schools have seen student attendance rates of around 72% on average and teacher attendance rates of approximately 85% on average. (Source: Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)-2018)

The Following are Some of the Challenges Urban Indian Education is Facing

The Indian education system is expanding at a rapid rate, and the government has made a number of steps to improve the education system. Despite these steps, however, schools in urban regions continue to struggle with variety of issues. The items in the following list are among the most important in history challenges that urban schools now face:

In many schools located in urban regions, there is an absence of necessary infrastructural amenities. Lack of transportation facilities is one of the most significant challenges that students who attend schools located in urban areas must contend with. Children are forced to travel a significant distance in order to get to better and affordable school since there are insufficient transportation options accessible for such long distance. As a result, the children stopped attending school, which is one of the primary challenges faced by educational institutions in urban areas. When compared to metropolitan regions, the number of educational institutions available in rural areas is significantly lower but due to government efforts now children from rural area are getting better and cheap education than to the urban children. The number of educational institutions that can be found in urban areas is much fewer compared to the need of appropriate metropolitan locations. Schools in urban locations typically lack the resources necessary to provide students with opportunities to participate in extracurricular activities outside of the classroom, including things like sports and cultural events. Facilities for “information & communication technology (ICT)” are found in urban educational institutions but costs high.

Suggestions to Enhance the Quality of Education in India's Urban Areas

Indian urban education might be improved in the following ways:

Both the number of schools in the urban area & transit options needs to be improved. Hostel facilities should be made available to the local students at affordable rates so that the problem of transportation may be avoided. The facilities needed for “information & communication technology (ICT)” should be made available

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at schools located in urban regions at affordable costs. Visual aids such as projectors, televisions, and other similar devices can be utilized in order to entice a bigger number of pupils and pique their interest in studying. Frequent get-togethers for parents should be held, and instructors should do everything they can to convince parents of the importance of education for their children.

Conclusion

Education is the single most important factor in every nation's ability to prosper and advance. Every kid has "the right to an education". This is "a human right". The Constitution of India stipulates that child of all castes and creeds, as well as those living in any part of the nation, are required to get a good education and that this education must be provided free of charge. Because of this, the Indian government passed "The Right to Education Act, 2009," which mandates that all children must attend primary school. However, if we take a look at the situation of the education sector in India, we can see that there is a significant divide among urban & rural education sector. Access to school remains a significant obstacle for many pupils living in urban regions, who must contend with a wide range of difficulties as discussed above. As a result, the government need to place a greater emphasis on educational initiatives in urban areas too. In addition, the government, in conjunction with other non- governmental organisations, educated young people, and instructors, should organise a specific awareness campaign in urban regions in order to raise affordable education for all theurban students.

References

- [1] Annual status of education report-2018. Retrieved from <https://img.asercentre.org/docs/ASER%202018/Release%20Material/aserreport2018.pdf2>
- [2] Arawat, S., Chettri, (2015) A Study on urban education in Darjeeling. *International Journal of science and research*. 4(3):2469-2472.
- [3] Das, D., Samanta, S (2014) Urban education in India: As an engine of sustainable urban development. *International journal of research in humanities, arts and literature*. 2(10):75-80
- [4] Govindarajan, S. (2017) A study on the urban education and urban development in India. *Shanlax* 6(1):106-114.
- [5] Hazra, A (2011) The challenges of educating urban India. *Kurukshetra*. 59 (7).
- [6] Urban education in India. Retrieved from <https://gradesfixer.com/free-essay-examples/urbaneducation-in-india/>
- [7] Sahapur, P, N., Omprakash, H, M (2017) Urban education in India: A scenario. *Scholarly research journal for interdisciplinary studies*. 4(31):5268-5272.
- [8] Sreekanthachari, G, J., Nagaraja, G (2013) An overview of urban education in India. *Advanced research journal of social science*. 4(1):115-119.
- [9] Study of education in urban India. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/education/study-of-education-in-urban-india-educationessay.php>

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PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

We all know that every child is unique in his or her own way. Some are bright, and some are dull. But regardless of these differences, everyone has an equal right to develop their potential. Inclusive education protects the right of all disabled students, ensuring that all children, whether disabled or not, receive the opportunity to be part of the regular classroom. Inclusive education has been noted as a key policy to promote the education of all children in society. Specifically, all children, regardless of gender, race and ethnic background, will be given equal opportunity to enjoy their right to education. In achieving this goal, parents have been noted as key actors who will support their children in enjoying their right to education, and they are the first to know the child and the ones who will be involved in their lives as their children move from primary to middle to high school. Parental involvement is the foundation of every child's progress in school, and they continue to influence their children learning and development throughout their lives. The main purpose of this paper is to describe the involvement of parents in inclusive education because parental involvement is an important part of making inclusive education work.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Parental Involvement, Child, Role and Advantages.*

Introduction

The child-parent relationship has a significant impact on most aspects of a child's development when optimal parenting practices and behaviours have a positive impact on children's self-esteem, academic scores, cognitive development, and behavioural traits. Parents serve as role models for their children. Parents play an important role in the difficult and dynamic process of inclusion, which begins with their choice to integrate their child into society at large. Children with and without disabilities learn together in an inclusive setting where everyone is treated equally. This strategy differs from more conventional methods of educating children with impairments, which involve putting them in distinct classes or even separate schools. Teachers, parents, and governments at all agree that inclusive education is a better way to guarantee that children with and without disabilities attain their full educational potential, and UNCRPD Article 24 specifically mentions it. Parents are, as we all know, their children's first teachers, and they continue to influence their children's learning and development throughout their lives. So, today's requirement is that parents of disabled children have a say in how education should be provided to children with disabilities.

I believe that without the cooperation of parents, inclusive education cannot function smoothly. Teachers should try to motivate parents to admit children with disabilities because parents sometimes over protect the child or the child experiences a state of neglect. Experience has also shown in India that parents of disabled children either over protect or neglect the children due to the confused stage and fear of having a child with disabilities at home. They also have apprehensions about coping with the educational and social needs of a child with a disability. Parents have to be oriented in such a way that they develop a positive attitude toward the overall development of the child. If needed, they can be brought to institutions for people with disabilities for observation and also for interaction with other disabled students. In many programmes in the country, groups of parents provide the main support for the education of children with disabilities. The parents themselves can work as agents for fostering the value of non-discrimination in the case of a disabled child.

Goals of Parental Involvement

The following are the goals of parental involvement. To make sure that parents of children with to ensure that special needs are treated equally parents receive equitable treatment as members of their child's educational team and are involved included in decisions that affect the school community. Throughout the course of a student's academic career, it is critical to encourage parent's involvement in the public education system. Parents' should out to be treated as full considered complete team members and included in decision-making regarding decisions made about their children's education educational needs. Establishing fair, appreciative and child-centered Creating communication between parents and the school that is equitable, appreciative, and child-centered. Encourage parents to take an active role in their impaired children's education by providing psychosocial support. A proactive approach to instructional guidelines and subject matter.

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Role and Responsibilities of Parents towards Inclusion

Home is the only place a youngster can receive the assistance needed for its growth and development is at home. The education of students with disabilities also benefits from the involvement of parents and other family members. Children's education is also influenced by family and culture. Any family is society's first school; parents are a child's first teacher. Parents are crucial in helping their kids to grow up and go from being impaired to becoming able-bodied. The requirements of the child are entirely the parent's responsibility. Parents' obligations to children with disabilities include the following. The disabled children should remain in a cordial connection. Supporting their child's involvement in numerous activities and encouraging support. Providing chances for their kids to interact with the adults. Parents should talk about their child's goal, needs, and hobbies. The parents should have complete knowledge about their child's disability. The impairment of their child should be completely known to the parents. The educational programs and plans have to have been chosen in advance.

Benefits of Inclusive Education

The following are some benefits of inclusive education. All children are able to be part of can participate in their community, develop, have a sense feeling of belonging, and become better prepared, and improve their readiness for life in the community life as both children as and adults. It provides better opportunities for learning. Children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children. Better learning chances are offered by it. When they learn in classrooms alongside other kids, kids of all levels are frequently more motivated to learn. The expectations of all the children archive higher aspirations. Successful inclusion attempts to develop individuals' strengths and gifts. Aims to maximize each person's talents and strengths. It promotes parental involvement in their children's education and in the goings-on at their neighborhood schools. Children can concentrate on their own objectives while interacting with other pupils their own age. Teachers that are creative may seek out novel ways to teach or create classes that include all students. Children can participate. Creativity may mean teachers looking to teach in different ways or designing their lessons so that all children can be involve.

Benefits of the Parental Involvement

The following are some benefits of parental involvement in inclusive education. Parents are the first teacher of their children. So, children are motivated by them easily. They should encourage kids to make friends with their classmates or kids in the neighborhood. Parents can encourage their kids to take part in activities where they can interact with kids own age who have different skills and meet new ones. Even better, they can conduct an internet search for organizations that provide activities that the kid could be interested in. Parents should support their kids in making friends with their classmates and kids in the neighborhood. Before the start of the school year, parents can decide on the child's educational plans by discussing the child's goals, expectations, and preferences with their teacher, therapist, etc. Parents must fully understand their child's entitlement to a diverse education. The school might forgo providing entertainment for the unique student. The parents should make an effort to articulate their reasons for favouring inclusive education for their child. Share information with families about the curriculum and academic success. Establish trustworthy, effective avenues for two-way communication between the home and the school.

Conclusion

Around the world, the concept of inclusive education is becoming more popular. The process of expanding student's participation in the cultural curriculum and mainstream communities is known as inclusive education. Finally, we may state that inclusion is about giving kids the support they require to learn and engage in meaningful activities. The secret is to do just offer assistance as required. A child has a right to inclusive education; it is not privilege. All children with disabilities should have access to the general education curriculum and should attend school alongside similarly aged children who are not impaired. Therefore, collaboration between specialists and parents of children with impairments results in the best results. Education for all (EFA) is the goal of inclusive education. Therefore, parental involvement in inclusive education is more crucial for kids and schools.

References

- [1] Anderson, K. J., &Minke, K. M. (2007). Parental involvement in education: Toward an understanding of parent's decision making. *The journal of educational research*, 100(5), 311-323.
- [2] Agarwal J.C. (2014). *Essentials of educational psychology*, Vikas publishing house.
- [3] Mangal S. K. (2018). *Advanced Educational Psychology*, PHI Learning private united.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

TRENDS IN TECHNICAL AND PROFESSIONAL COURSES IN INDIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Introduction

Multicultural education is a progressive approach in transforming education by exposing the shortcomings and failures of discriminatory practices in education. Multicultural societies need a holistic approach because the existence of cultural diversity requires system that can appreciate existing cultures. Besides the society, Multicultural education is built by developing synergistic knowledge, which creates new perceptions in the face of knowledge development. Through creative and innovative strategies, multicultural education is being optimized in the environment of higher education institutions. With multicultural education, students will get a global perspective on facing various problems in the industrial revolution era. Holistic education focuses on developing universal human values and nurtures the understanding and respect crucial to living harmoniously in society.

Technical Education

The Technical Courses in India became significant with the establishment of the All India Council for Technical Education and today the council conducts a long list of Technical Courses in India. Most of the Technical Courses in India are conducted in the Technical Institutes in India. The vocational courses offered by the various technical and polytechnic institutions include variety of courses that include degrees, diplomas and post-diploma vocational education in both technical and non-technical disciplines. The AICTE-Act was constituted to provide for the establishment of an All India Council for Technical Education with a view to proper planning and co-ordinated development of a technical education system throughout the country, the promotion of qualitative improvements of such education in relation to planned quantitative growth, and regulation & proper maintenance of norms and standards in the technical education system and for the matters connected therewith.

Technical Courses in India

The demand for skilled professionals is so high level so that some Technical Courses are being conducted in India such as vocational training, diploma courses in Catering Management, Home Science, and many similar courses. Moreover, very effective and beneficial trending courses are introduced with various fields of engineering and agriculture.

Engineering

This is by far one of the most prevalent courses in the country now. Reports suggest that engineering is also one field which has the maximum number of employment opportunities. India has many engineering and technical institutes which provide courses in engineering at undergraduate, post-graduate and doctorate levels.

Management Courses

Next to engineering courses, management courses are also very popular with the students. Various colleges and universities offer management courses in undergraduate (BBA), Post-graduate (MBA), diploma and Doctorate courses. The biggest advantages with these courses are that once the students are done with the courses, they can easily get recruited in multinational companies at very high salaries.

Mass Media and Communication Courses

Nowadays, Journalism and Mass Communication courses are too popular. Whether it is print media or broadcast. A journalism course can prepare a journalist to be a good editor, a writer and help them to be adept at handling the camera behind and in front of the scene. The journalism industry has many opportunities for aspiring reporters, editors in fields like newspaper, News channels, agencies, publishing houses, PR companies etc.

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Computer Courses

One of the most revolutionary inventions, the computer has changed the professional industry by a huge amount. The IT industry has boomed unconditionally and now demands a lot of professionals in this field. There is an urgent need for people who are deft at handling the computer and its various nuances. It is a lucrative career and demands professionals in various computer applications in private as well as government sectors.

Hotel Management

Hotel Management is a specialized degree for professionals who wants to be part of the hotel, hospitality and industry. It trains people in all aspects of managing a hotel – whether a five star hotel or a small beach-side resort. Hotel Management jobs require a range of skills including Food and Beverage Service, Front Office operation, Sales and Marketing, Events, Banquets, Accounting etc.

Agricultural Courses

Agriculture courses involve the study of various technical and scientific subjects related to agricultural technology, food technology, dairy industry, food science, plant science, horticulture and even forestry. The main difference between these fields is their area of focus.

Professional Education

Education is a never-ending learning loop. It will continue after graduation and the commencement of a profession. Continuing education allows career-minded people to develop their abilities and become more professional at what they do. It is especially important for boarding school administrators in the field of primary and secondary education management to provide opportunities for teachers to grow professionally, not only to provide the best learning results for their students but also to be more effective and fulfilled in other aspects of their jobs.

Need for a Professional Course in Today's World

Today's world is a very competitive and everyone needs to stay up-to-date. By Support Education i-connect Online website, either its education or technology with the demand of circumstances. Every student in today's world is aware of his/ her desire and interest. They mostly choose the course that they like and pursue them for higher studies and in the end get the job of their dreams. Most of the teaching that takes place in these professional courses is very intensive, specific and subject oriented. In other colleges where the degree courses happen, the teaching is more relaxed and generalized. After passing a professional course, the entry to various careers become easier as most of them require certification at the entry-level.

Professional Courses in India

Nowadays, the best and the most popular professional courses are introduced in Indian educational system. Such as some of them are given the below.

Medical Courses

MBBS, BDS, AYUSH, B. Pharm, D. Pharm, and NURSING are some of the specialized courses that the professional colleges provide. This is one of the most respected careers and every year hundreds and thousands of doctors emerge from these courses. They provide classes in all levels-undergraduate, post-graduate, Ph. D levels and even specializations in the subjects of choice. Specialization after MBBS or MD is very necessary because the demand is mostly for doctors who are adept in a single field. NEET selection test is done every year in the long stretch of April from the subjects Physics, Chemistry, and Biology.

Law

Law means the system of rules which a particular country or community recognizes as regulating the actions of its members and which it may enforce by the imposition of penalties. Law, the discipline and profession concerned with the customs, practices, and rules of conduct of a community that are recognized as binding by the community. Enforcement of the body of rules is through a controlling authority.

Bachelor of Education

B.Ed is a necessary course for anyone to enter into the school level of teaching. The B. Ed syllabus is designed to help the candidates not only gain knowledge about the different teaching methods but also gain the other soft skills such as counselling to understand the psyche of the students. The course also helps in the

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development of a better academic system at the basic level.

Chartered Accountant (CA)

Chartered accountant is one of the most outstanding expert courses in India. Crafted by a Chartered accountant in fields of business, monetary book keepers, charge book keepers, evaluation, general administration and spending experts, and so forth. Science and Arts stream understudies are additionally qualified for this course and seek after a profession in the field of CA. In the wake of passing class twelfth, give a Common Proficiency Test (CPT) test. These tests pose various decision inquiries from four subjects Fundamentals of Accounting, Mercantile Laws, General Economics, and Quantitative Aptitude.

Psychologist

Psychologists are trained in observing, analysing and understanding human behaviour. Based on their understanding of a patients' emotions and mental processes, psychologists treat their behavioural or emotional problems through counselling and therapy. They are mental health professionals who have not done a medical degree and cannot prescribe medicine. Child Psychology, Counselling Psychology, Organizational / Industrial Psychology, Sports Psychology, Educational Psychology, Social Psychology are some of the specializations in Psychology.

Tourism

Just like hospitality, tourism business or profession has gained a lot of popularity as the number of tourist destinations have increased and also people have started exploring the world more. For any country, tourism is a great source of income, hence it can be said that making a career in it is a great move. One can do various courses in Tourism to remain a notch higher. Many Institutes all over the country provide certificate courses in Travel and Tourism.

Fashion Designer

Style planning is a type of conduct craftsmanship, which has improved our garments, adornments, and way of life, and so forth. The present time style planner requests increment step by step in government or privately owned businesses, Hollywood, Bollywood, and other entertainment worlds.

Conclusion

Technical, Vocational and Professional education plays a vital role in the development of the individual and of the society. Constitutional amendment transferring education from the State list to the concurrent list. National Education policy implement General Education Council (GEC), to frame "graduate attributes", namely the learning outcomes expected. It will also be responsible in framing a National Higher Education Qualification Framework (NHEQF). The National Council for Teacher Education will come under the GEC, as a professional standard-setting body (PSSB). Other PSSBs will include professional councils such as the Veterinary Council of India, Council of Architecture, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, and National Council for Vocational Education and Training.

References

- [1] Aggarwal, A., Mehta, S., Gupta, D., Sheikh, S., Pallagatti, S., Singh, R., & Singla, I. (2012). Dental Students' Motivations and Perceptions of Dental Professional Career in India. *Journal of Dental Education*, 76(11), 1532–1539. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.0022-0337.2012.76.11.tb05416.x>
- [2] Goel, V. (2009). Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) system in India for sustainable development. Ministry of Human Resource Development Report, 1–21. http://adapt.it/adapt-indice-a-z/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/VT_Sustainable_Dev.pdf
- [3] Johnson, E. J., Bailey, K., & Padmore, J. (2012). Issues and challenges of social work practicum in Trinidad and Tobago and India. *Caribbean Teaching Scholar*, 2(1), 19–29.
- [4] N, S., AS, A., & M, S. (2015). Professional Development in Education in India: A View. *Journal of Political Sciences & Public Affairs*, 03(03). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2332-0761.1000173>
- [5] Pati, S., Sinha, R., Panda, M., Pati, S., Sharma, A., & Zodpey, S. (2017). Global health teaching in India: A curricular landscape. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 5(SEP), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00259>
- [6] Sharma, A., Sahu, R., Kasar, P., & Sharma, R. (2014). Internet addiction among professional courses students: A study from central India. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, 3(9), 1069. <https://doi.org/10.5455/ijmsph.2014.180620142>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

THE BENEFITS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: PROMOTING AN EQUITABLE AND ACCESSIBLE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This article examines the benefits of inclusive education for students, families, and schools, and reviews recent research on the advantages of promoting an equitable and accessible learning environment. The article argues that inclusive education is beneficial in that it fosters a greater sense of safety, acceptance, and belonging for all students, promotes acceptance of diversity, increases access to learning, and creates a more supportive learning environment. Furthermore, it highlights the role of parents, teachers, and administrators in supporting the success of students in an inclusive setting, and examines the potential risks and challenges associated with inclusive education. The article concludes by emphasizing the need for ongoing research and dialogue on inclusive education approaches and strategies.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Equity, Accessibility, Learning Environment, Safety*

Introduction

Over the past two decades, inclusive education has become increasingly popular as a way of providing an equitable and accessible learning environment for all students, regardless of their race, gender, ability, background, or economic status. The benefits of inclusive education are numerous, and can be seen in both academic and social settings. Inclusive education promotes a greater sense of safety, acceptance, and belonging for all students. It also fosters respect for diversity and helps to ensure that all students have access to learning materials and appropriate instructional strategies. In addition, it creates a more supportive learning environment, which is beneficial to all students, regardless of their levels of ability or disability. It has become evident that traditional methods of teaching and learning do not provide equitable learning opportunities for all students. The concept of inclusive education focuses on meeting the needs of all learners, regardless of their disability, race, gender, ethnicity, language, social and economic status. This essay will explore the benefits of inclusive education, including increased student engagement, improved academic achievement, increased access to resources, and a more equitable learning environment. We will also discuss how these benefits are being realized in the classroom and what measures educators can take to ensure that all students are receiving equitable access to the educational opportunities they deserve.

Objectives

The major objectives of the paper are given below;

- 1) To critically analyze the advantages of inclusive education for students of all backgrounds.
- 2) To explore the ways in which inclusive education can provide equitable access to learning opportunities.
- 3) To consider the challenges that may arise in implementing an inclusive education system.
- 4) To identify strategies to ensure a successful implementation of an inclusive education system.
- 5) To examine the role of teachers in fostering an inclusive learning environment.
- 6) To discuss the potential benefits of inclusive education on student well-being and academic achievement.

Definition of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is defined as an educational system that includes all students, regardless of their ability, race, gender, ethnicity, religion, or social and economic status. It is an important part of ensuring that all students have access to a quality education and that discrimination and exclusion are minimized. In an inclusive education system, all students are provided equal access to the same educational resources, including curriculum, instruction, assessment, and support.

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Increased Student Engagement

Inclusion provides a more welcoming, supportive, and engaging learning environment for all students. In an inclusive classroom, all students have access to the same level of instruction and resources. This encourages students to participate more actively in the learning process, as they feel that they can contribute to and benefit from the class. Additionally, students who are included in the general education classroom are less likely to experience isolation or stigmatization and are more likely to form meaningful relationships with their peers.

Improved Academic Achievement

Inclusion in the classroom has also been shown to improve academic achievement. Research has demonstrated that students who are included in the general education classroom are more likely to meet or exceed standards and are less likely to be retained or require special education services. This is likely due to the fact that students in an inclusive classroom have access to the same resources and instruction as their peers, providing them with the opportunity to reach their full academic potential.

Increased Access to Resources

Inclusion also provides students with an increased access to resources. In an inclusive classroom, all students have access to the same curriculum, instruction, assessment, and support. This ensures that all students have the opportunity to gain the skills and knowledge necessary for success in the classroom and beyond. Additionally, it provides students with the opportunity to develop social skills, such as collaboration, communication, and problem-solving, which are essential for success in the workplace.

The Role of Parents, Teachers, and Administrators

Parents, teachers, and administrators have the potential to play a key role in the success of their students in an inclusive setting. Parents can provide support to their children in the form of advocacy, guidance, and emotional support. Teachers can help to ensure that students have access to appropriate learning materials and strategies, as well as provide a safe and welcoming environment in which to learn. Administrators should ensure that all students have access to appropriate resources and programs, while also providing support to teachers in their implementation of inclusive practices.

Importance of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is an important aspect of the educational system that seeks to ensure that all students, regardless of their abilities, can fully access and participate in the learning process. It recognizes the right of all learners to be in the same classroom and to participate in the same activities, regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, and/or beliefs. Inclusive education promotes a sense of belonging and a sense of community among all students, which can have a positive impact on their academic and social development. By providing a safe and supportive environment, inclusive education helps to create a culture of acceptance, respect, and appreciation for the differences among students. Inclusive education also helps to foster a sense of self-worth and self-confidence in students, which can lead to greater academic success. Finally, inclusive education can help to reduce the number of students who drop out of school or become disengaged from the learning process. By providing a supportive and welcoming learning environment, inclusive education can play an important role in helping all students reach their full potential.

Benefits of Inclusive Education

The benefits of inclusive education have been widely recognized and many studies have demonstrated the positive outcomes associated with the implementation of inclusive education programs. These benefits include increased student engagement, improved academic achievement, increased access to resources, and a more equitable learning environment. There are numerous benefits of inclusive education, which include greater safety, acceptance, and belonging for all students. Students are more likely to feel safe and accepted in an inclusive environment, as it allows for greater visibility and celebration of individual differences.

Furthermore, inclusive education can help to ensure that all students have access to learning materials and appropriate instructional strategies, which can help to improve educational outcomes. Inclusive education also helps to foster respect for diversity, as students are exposed to a variety of perspectives, backgrounds, and experiences. In addition, an inclusive learning environment can be beneficial for all students by creating a more supportive learning environment. Through such an environment, students can learn to collaborate, problem solve, and think critically. Finally, in an inclusive setting, students are more likely to be taught in a manner that is appropriate to their individual needs and abilities, which can help to increase academic success.

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Potential Risks and Challenges

While inclusive education can provide many benefits, there are also potential risks and challenges associated with it. For example, teachers may require additional training to ensure that they are able to effectively implement inclusive practices. In addition, there may be challenges in providing adequate resources for all students to ensure that they have access to the same opportunities for learning. Finally, there may be logistical issues with creating an inclusive learning environment, such as difficulties in accommodating all students in the same physical space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, inclusive education has the potential to provide numerous benefits to students, families, and schools. It can promote a greater sense of safety, acceptance, and belonging for all students, foster respect for diversity, and create a more supportive learning environment. Furthermore, it can help to ensure that all students have access to learning materials and appropriate instructional strategies, and set the stage for successful academic outcomes. It is important for parents, teachers, and administrators to be aware of the potential risks and challenges associated with inclusive education, and to play an active role in supporting and promoting these practices in their schools and communities. In conclusion, inclusive education is beneficial in providing an equitable and accessible learning environment for all students, regardless of their abilities or differences. Through the implementation of inclusive practices, students with diverse abilities and backgrounds learn to appreciate and respect one another, thereby fostering a sense of community and promoting cooperation. Additionally, students of all abilities are able to benefit from an inclusive education by receiving the same instruction and opportunities to succeed. Finally, inclusive education promotes a sense of acceptance and belonging to those who may otherwise feel excluded or marginalized. Ultimately, inclusive education has the potential to create a better and more equitable learning environment for all.

References

- [1] Ainscow, M. (2016). *Inclusive education: A global agenda*. Routledge. Cummings,
- [2] W., & Packer, M. (2020). *Inclusion: Accommodating all students in the general education classroom*. Corwin Press.
- [3] Cunningham, A., & Thomas, B. (2015). *Inclusive education: A practical guide to supporting diversity in the classroom*. Routledge.
- [4] Department for Education (2020). *Inclusion and special educational needs: A guide for parents and carers*.retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/inclusion-and-special-educational-needs-a-guide-for-parents-and-carers>
- [5] and carers.
- [6] Hall, C. (2018). *The inclusive classroom: effective strategies for reaching all learners*. Association for Supervision & Curriculum Development.
- [7] Jarrell, S. (2018). *Inclusive education: A guide to implementing the practice*. Oxford University Press.
- [8] Kirton, G., & Ziegler, D. (2017). *Inclusive education: Policies and practices*. Routledge.
- [9] McMillan, J.H., & Schumacher, S. (2010). *Research in education: Evidence-based inquiry* (7th ed.). Pearson.

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NEP 2020: TOWARDS A INCLUSIVE AND HOLISTIC APPROACH TO EDUCATION

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Abstract

India ratified the United Nations Agenda for Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4), intends to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all". Since the existing educational system was insufficient to achieve the desired long-term goal, the Indian government proposed the New Education Policy (NEP) in 2020. The researcher has carefully examined the documents of the previous education commission, policies, committees, and relevant literature that are pertinent to this research. The outcomes of this article will assist its readers in comprehending the context to propose inclusive and holistic educational approach in NEP 2020; and also the reader will comprehend the stream of change in education policy, and he/she will be aware of the history of inclusive education in brief. The novelty of this conceptual research is to understand the significance of the holistic educational approach in the contemporary educational curriculum and system. Moreover, readers will be able to recognise and understand how much important an inclusive educational approach is for survival, as this is the ultimate objective of all education.

Key words: *National Education Policy 2020, Inclusive education, Holistic education, Approach to Education.*

Introduction

India's New Education Policy (NEP2020) is a historic initiative and the first panoramic policy under Modi's regime in thirty-four years. The goal of the NEP is to provide a framework to direct the advancement and progression of education in the country. Post colonial, Indian education system undergoes a number of changes in order to make it more accessible to all citizens. Several commissions, policies, and schemes worked well to make education more holistic and inclusive. This is India's third education policy after independence. NEP 2020 is the result of over 2 lakh suggestions from various levels including, local self-government, 2.5 lakh gramme panchayats, 6,600 blocks, 6,000 ULBs, and 676 districts. There is no doubt that holistic productivity is most significant in 21st century job market. The NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance equitable, inclusive, education and creates contributing citizens for building a plural society with a GER of 50% by 2035.

Education of disadvantaged and differently able people is no longer a privilege. It is the right of the child and mandatory responsibility of the country. Education has supreme importance in developing countries especially; country likes India because it has its own potentiality to make the country super power. But India fails to provide education to every child in each and every corner of the country. In India, inclusive education has been described as excluding children with disabilities. Disabled children hardly ever complete primary school, and only 9% complete secondary school. Approximately 45% of disabled people are illiterate. Based on the statistics, only 62.9% of people with disability aged between 3 to 35 have ever got regular education. Specific disability like autism, cerebral palsy, and genders (girls with disabilities) are disproportionately affected, that means they are less likely to be enrolled in mainstream education. Various policies on inclusive education, such as the RPwD Act 2016, have been introduced by the Government of India over the years. Despite the fact that all policies emphasized the right of children from diverse backgrounds and abilities to access formal education, disparities persisted. Finally, after 34 years, we have our long-awaited National Education Policy. The National Education Policy 2020 envisions a structural and inclusive change in the educational system. It emphasized on 'Equitable and Inclusive Education' in the country. This evokes the idea that no child should be denied educational opportunities based on of their background or socio-cultural identity. An education system that focuses on the overall growth of students is the most effective way to prepare students for a productive and competitive world. NEP 2020, made emphasis on inclusive and holistic education, it take drastic turn in the system of education of the country. Previously, mainstream education entirely focused on rote memorization, and theoretical knowledge that couldn't be applied productively and constructively in real-life or real world situations. This article tries to draw the inclusive and holistic approach of education in the light of NEP2020.

Objectives

- 1) To understand importance of inclusive education in the light of NEP 2020.
- 2) To identify the significance of holistic education to the 'all-round development' of the students.

Methodology

The researchers have chosen conceptual research method to establish their view point on the inclusive and holistic approach to education in the light of NEP 2020. It abstract concepts and ideas from existing documents and interpret existing reports, documents and concepts in a different way.

International Scenario of Inclusive Education

Conceptual frameworks and philosophy of inclusive education vary across countries. To figure out the success or failure of curricular, instructional, and social inclusion, contextual differences must be considered. As a result, the notion that 'effective method' for inclusive education can exist in a coherent and measurable form is completely inaccurate. Inclusion is highly contextual and resists educational approach or instructional techniques that attempt to implement methodologies or strategies to schools and the activities that take place within them. Internationally, the emphasis placed on education as a fundamental right of every individual began 60 years ago with both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 and the World Declaration for Education for All in 1990. Various International Conventions, such as the Convention against Discrimination in 1960, the Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1989, which was the first treaty developed for child rights, and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) in 2006, proclaimed the need for equality of opportunity. Schuelka, Johnstone (2012), state that, Salamanca Framework (1994) and Biwako Millennium Framework of Action (2002) are two important International Frameworks for raising awareness of inclusive educations. According to Salamanca Statement (1994) main purpose of inclusive education, "Regular schools with this inclusive orientation are the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society and achieving education for all; moreover, they provide an effective education to the majority of children and improve the efficiency and ultimately the cost-effectiveness of the entire education system."

Historical Perspective of Inclusive Education in India

Special education started in India as a separate system of education for disabled children outside of the mainstream education system in the 1880s. In 1883, first school for the deaf in Bombay, and 1887 first school for the blind in Amritsar were established. After independence there were increases in the number of schools for this special people such as 32 schools for the blind, 30 for the deaf, and 3 for the mentally retarded. Based on 2020-2021 statistics, there were abundant growth in number of schools like in Primary level 4,576, Middle level 3,525, High level 579 and Higher Secondary level 135 but this is not a sufficient number to accommodate all children in the specialized category. However, as the number of these special schools increased, certain disadvantages became increasingly obvious. These institutions reached out largely to the urban and middle-upper family not for every corner of the country and not cost effective for all. Most importantly, these schools segregated children from the mainstream, resulting in the development of a distinct disability culture.

Legislation and Policy Initiatives

The Preamble of the Indian Constitution (26 November 1949) states that everyone has the right to equality of status and opportunity. Article 41 of the Constitution's Directive Principles supports the right to education, work and public assistance in certain situation it also include disability. Furthermore, Article 45 commits to provision of free and compulsory education to all children up to the age of fourteen. The 86th Amendment Act of 2002 incorporated Article 21-A into the Indian Constitution to provide free and compulsory education to all children aged six to fourteen years as a Fundamental Right in such a manner as the State may by law determine. The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009, which represents the consequential legislation envisaged under Article 21- A, states that every child has a right to full-time elementary education of satisfactory and equitable quality in a formal school that meets certain essential norms and standards. In India, the Kothari Education Commission (1964-66) emphasized the importance of developing an effective education for individuals with disabilities in order to guarantee equal educational opportunities and also on the recommendation of commission Prime Minister, Smt. Indira Gandhi proposed India's first educational policy in 1968. It proclaimed "Educational facilities for physically and mentally handicapped children should be expanded, and efforts should be made to develop integrated programmes allowing handicapped children to study in mainstream schools". The Planning Commission (1971) of India included an integrated education programme. In 1974 The Government of India launched a scheme called Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) to put the concept of integration into action. This was the first exclusive scheme with the vision was to promote the inclusion of children with mild to moderate disabilities in regular schools. The 42nd Constitutional amendment (in 1976) added education to the concurrent list. India's second education policy was implemented in 1986. It emphasizes Inclusive

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Education and states that "children with mild disabilities should be permitted to attend regular school, while children with moderate to severe disabilities should continue to attend special school". The Mental Health Act of 1987 went into effect, amending the Indian Lunacy Act of 1912 in order to consolidate the law for mentally ill people. In the same year, the Project Integrated Education for the Disabled (PIED) was launched to promote neighborhood schools to enroll individual with disabilities. This was collaboration between the Education Ministry, NCERT, and UNICEF.

The Programme of Action (1992) clearly indicated that "the children disabilities that can be integrated in the regular school must get education there and the children who are facing problem in integrating in the regular school must send to the special. They could have transferred to a regular school after learning skills". In September 1992, the Rehabilitation Council of India Act (RCI) was also passed. This act was enacted to regulate rehabilitation professional training and the regular maintenance of a Central Rehabilitation Register. Following the RCI Act, the Persons with Disabilities Act was passed in 1995, guaranteeing full participation and equality for individuals with disabilities in the Asian and Pacific Region. The District Primary Education Program was launched in 1997 with the collaboration of the Government of India and the World Bank. According to the DPEP, "any difference that a child exhibited in learning was to be attributed not to a problem with the child, but with the school system." This was the first time the emphasis was on school readiness (DPEP, 1997). The National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Mental Retardation, Cerebral Palsy, and Multiple Disabilities Act was passed in 1999. Various schemes, such as the "Reach and Relief Scheme," are in place to provide financial assistance to people with the four disabilities mentioned above.

In 2001, the Government of India launched the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) to promote the universalization of primary education. But while SSA was not a disability-specific intervention scheme, the main focus was on Education for All. The Inclusive Education of the Disabled at the Secondary Stage (IEDSS) Act was passed in 2009. This was a revamped IEDC for secondary education. The Government of India launched the Rastriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA) for the Universalization of Secondary Education the same year.

Inclusive Education in NEP 2020

After 34 years, the National Education Policy was released in accordance with the recommendation of the Kasturirangan Committee. This is a comprehensive policy that addresses all levels of education in the country. The policy was divided into four sections and twenty seven subsections. Inclusive and equitable education discussed under the school education of the document. NEP 2020 is coherent with the RPwD Act of 2016. According to the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act (2016), "inclusive education is a "system of education in which students with and without disabilities learn together and the system of teaching and learning is suitably adapted to meet the learning needs of different types of students with disabilities." Banga, (2015) observed that, the RPwD act also confirmed the provision of free education for disabled children up to the age of 18 in a suitable environment. In addition, the Act increased the 3% reservation to 5% for people with benchmark disabilities (21 disabilities list in Act) in all government institutions of higher learning. The person with benchmark disability is defined as anyone who has at least 40% of the listed 21 disabilities in the RPwD Act. As a non-discrimination measure, the Act also emphasized barrier-free access (Narayan, John 2017). The NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance of inclusive and equitable education across all levels. It recognizes various groups as Socio-Economic Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs). A number of factors have influenced the enrollment and retention rates of Scheduled Caste children, including poverty, lack of access to good schools, social inequality, societal norms and traditions, and language. Children from Scheduled Tribes, on the other hand, faced challenges due to historical and geographical factors. NPE recommended a number of approaches to address the issues, which included an open school, bicycles, walking and cycling group, technology interventions, and adequate barrier-free infrastructure.

Holistic Education in NEP 2020

The NEP 2020 has rearranged school education's curriculum and pedagogy to a 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 design in order to make them adaptive and relevant to the educational needs and interests of learners at different stages of their development. Moreover, there is no parallel changes to the physical infrastructure will be required. The policy aims to develop engaged, productive, and contributing citizens who will contribute to the development of an, inclusive, equitable and plural society as outlined by our Constitution. NEP incorporates significant comprehensive intervention strategies to make the learning process more robust and holistic. India has a long and glorious history of multidisciplinary approaches to learning and teaching. Rigveda, too, acknowledges and illustrates the possibility of unbounded learning by focusing on various aspects of education. This system was illustrated by ancient institutions such as Nalanda and Takshashila, that also taught almost every branch of knowledge such as, painting, singing, mathematics, chemistry, , vocational courses

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which including, carpentry, clothing making, and professional fields including such engineering, medicine, , and soft skills like as communication., debate, and discussion.. In recent years, the emphasis has shifted to specialization in specific subjects or disciplines, resulting in the growth and development of single stream institutions. However, the broader learning system continued to narrow over the centuries. The NEP aims at developing and fostering multidisciplinary education because it is known to nurture vibrant communities of scholars, scientists, thinkers, and inventors, by enabling students to develop into well-rounded individuals those who are smart enough to think holistically about world around them.

Conclusion

The New Education Policy 2020 is a watershed moment in Indian education. However some innovative initiatives have been taken in this policy to improve the education system, it also has a correlation to international education. The experts in the field planned the policy according to the need and demand of modern education. They have evaluated the extent of the situation in the context of global education. India is attempting to raise educational quality and standards to the mark of international standards. From segregation to inclusion, India's inclusive education system faces numerous challenges. It took a transformation of attitude to view the disability as a special ability. Therefore, the Indian government developed a new policy that considers inclusive education. If it properly implemented, the New Education Policy 2020 will serve as a catalyst for inclusive education. This signifies a paradigm change in inclusive education. All of the aspects of holistic and inclusive education discussed above will result in successful and high-quality education for all children in the country. It will help in reducing the discrepancy between expectations and reality of education in India.

Reference

- [1] Balasundaram (2005). The Journey Towards Inclusive Education in India. Retrieved January 24, 2023, from <http://www.jlidd.jp/>.
- [2] Badjanova, J. (2013). PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS VIEWS ON A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO FACILITATING THE ACQUISITION OF MUSICAL CULTURAL VALUES, *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 78ñ90, DOI: 10.2478/jtes-2013-0013.
- [3] DISE. The Education Commission 1966. Retrieved from January 24, 2023, from <http://udise.in/>.
- [4] MHRD. National Policy Education, 1968. Retrieved from January 24, 2023, from <https://www.mhrd.gov.in/>.
- [5] MHRD. National Education Policy 1986. Retrieved from January 24, 2023 from <https://www.mhrd.gov.in/>.
- [6] MHRD. Programme of Action 1992. Retrieved from January 24, 2023 from <https://www.mhrd.gov.in/>.
- [7] National Education Policy 2020, MHRD, Govt of India. 2020. Available from: https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf.
- [8] NCBI. Mental Health Act 1987. Retrieved from January 24, 2023 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.
- [9] NCBI. Rights of Person with Disability Act 2016. Retrieved from January 24, 2023 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.
- [10] Priyadarshini, A. & Dave, D. (2021). Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education through Open and Distance Learning to realise the vision of National Education Policy–2020, *Researchgate, UNIVERSITY NEWS*, 59(07) FEBRUARY.
- [11] Schuelka, Johnstone (2012). Global trends in meeting the educational rights of children with disabilities: From international institutions to local responses. Retrieved, from January 24, 2023 <https://core.ac.uk/>.

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN NALGONDA DISTRICT, TELUGANA

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Abstract

The present study aims to investigate emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students at the secondary level. Using random sampling technique 313 students, from the r secondary level in different systems of education, namely, Government and management schools are chosen. The Emotional Intelligence Scale has been used to assess the emotional intelligence and the marks scored in Science were taken from their Quarterly performance. The data collected is subjected to statistical analysis, namely, mean, standard deviation, 't'- test, , Correlation. Results show a positive significant correlation between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among the students. Further the students belonging to the Government schools have a higher level of emotional intelligence compared to students in management schools at the r secondary level. Similarly, mean score of boys emotional intelligence is greater than the girls' students and rural school students' achievement is equal to the urban school students' achievement.

Introduction

Emotional intelligence refers to an ability to recognize the meanings of emotion and their relationships and to reason and problem-solve on the basis of them. Emotional intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of those emotions, and manage them. Emotional intelligence also reflects abilities to join intelligence, empathy and emotions to enhance thought and understanding of interpersonal dynamics. Academic Achievement is known to depend upon many factors. Emotional intelligence is one of the important factors which influence the individual's academic achievement. Therefore, it is one of the important variables to be considered for the individual's academic success or failure. So development of Emotional intelligence is essential for academic achievement. The degree of children's emotional intelligence which will be influenced by his success or failure in the school situation will also be determined by the extent to which the child feels about his personal worth and about his achievement . For children who do not perform well, their failure reinforced the avoidant behavior and the academic achievement situation becomes student frustration, boredom and conflict with one's teacher and parents. The attempt made by the present study is to probe the relationship of emotional intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school students and to fill a gap in the existing literature on the subject. Thus as a kind of studying the emotional intelligence and achievement in science of secondary school students the study is taken.

Statement of the Problem

Building one's emotional intelligence has a lifelong impact. Many parents and educators, alarmed by increasing levels of conflict in young school children--from low self- esteem to early drug and alcohol use to depression, are rushing to teach students the skills necessary for emotional intelligence. Since emotional intelligence is a master aptitude, a capacity that profoundly affects all other abilities, either facilitating or interfering with them (Goleman, 1995), the need is felt to investigate the emotional intelligence and academic achievement among students. Hence the title of the study is " A Study on Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science of Secondary school students"

Need and Significance of the Study

Emotional intelligence is the capability of realizing our own emotions and also realizing others persons emotions properly. Emotionally intelligent person become sympathetic and empathetic to others persons various feelings and guide himself and other people properly in a critical situation, become calm and quite in every situations. According to Goleman "emotional intelligence" of a person helps him to get success in his educational life and professional life. To achieve academic success in life emotional intelligence plays an important role. Like other educational subjects emotional intelligence can be teach and improve among the students.

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Objectives

1. To study the level of Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students.
2. To study the difference in Emotional Intelligence with respect to Gender, Locality and Management
3. To study the difference in Achievement in Science with respect to Gender, Locality and Types of Institutions
4. To find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science of secondary school students
5. To find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science of secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality and Types of Institutions.

Variables

Emotional Intelligence, Science Achievement, Emotional Intelligence and Science Achievement

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality and Types of Institution
2. There is no significant difference in Achievement in Science of secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality and Types of institution
3. There is significant relationship between Emotional intelligence and Achievement in Science of secondary school students
4. There is significant relationship between Emotional intelligence and Achievement in Science of secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality and Types of institution

Methodology of Research

The study will adopt a Normative survey Method. The variables studied are the Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science. The sample consists of 300 IX standard students from both Government and management schools District. Emotional Intelligence questionnaire developed and validated by Researcher will be used for the study. Achievement score obtained from the school by the students is to be used for this study. The scores obtained were subject to statistical treatment using proper statistical technique. For this purpose Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' test, and Correlation were used. The results show obtained are interpreted and discussed in the light of problem factors to make the result meaningful.

Data Analysis

(i) Descriptive Analysis

Mean and Standard Deviation of the variable Emotional Intelligence

			Total Scores 332
Variable	N	Mean	SD
Emotional Intelligence	313	225.2	37.73
			Total Scores 332
Achievement in Science	313	56.37	18.67

(ii) Differential Analysis

1) Emotional Intelligence

Category	N	Mean	SD	't'	Sig.
Boys	160	232.88	35.08	0.022	NS
Girls	153	217.17	53.92		
Government	160	226.15	39.52	0.649	NS
Management	153	224.21	35.86		
Rural	160	229.92	36.17	0.023	NS
Urban	153	220.20	38.81		

2) Academic Achievement

Category	N	Mean	SD	't'	Sig.
Boys	160	28.72	18.83	0.023	NS
Girls	153	53.92	18.24		
Government	160	57.89	19.22	0.140	NS
Management	153	54.78	17.99		
Rural	160	56.16	18.29	0.836	NS
Urban	153	56.59	19.11		

3) Correlation Analysis

Variables	N	r	p
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science	313	0.738	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science – Boys	160	0.738	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science – Girls	153	0.733	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science-Government	160	0.741	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science-Management	153	0.736	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science-Rural	163	0.729	S
Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science-Urban	152	0.761	S

Findings

There is a medium level of Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students. Means score of boys Emotional intelligence is greater than the girl students. The students studying in Government schools are at a higher level than the students studying in management schools with respect to Emotional intelligence. Mean score of rural school students Emotional Intelligence is greater than the urban schools students. The Science achievement of secondary school students is medium level. The Science achievement of students studying in Government schools are at as higher level than students studying in management schools. Rural schools students achievement is equal to the urban school students achievement. There is no significance difference in Emotional Intelligence between boys and girls students, no significance difference between Government school students and management school students and there is no significance between rural school students and urban school students with respect to Emotional Intelligence. There is no difference between boys and girls of high school with respect to achievement in science, no significance difference

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between Government school students and management school students, no significance difference between rural and urban school students with respect to achievement in science. There is significance relationship between Emotional intelligence and Achievement in Science. There is a significance relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Science of boys, girls, Government, management, rural and urban high school students.

Educational Implications

The study reveals that there exists significant and positive relationship in academic achievement of secondary school students with respect to their emotional intelligence. The students should be motivated by their teachers and parents to maintain their academic achievement level. For the progress and development of our nation we need youth in every field. Therefore, we should take due care to enhance their academic achievement. In nutshell, a child's emotional life has an impact on child's academic success and social adaptation both in and out of the classroom. Teaching emotional skills and social skills is very important at school. It can affect academic achievement positively not only during the year they are taught, but during the years that follow as well. Teaching these skills has a long term effect on achievement. The emotions, feeling and values are for a person's achievement in life. Quality emotions and feeling help students to show their best potentials in the classroom. The study will help the policy makers and educationists to provide better provisions and opportunities to the students to achieve their goals in all areas from early schooling. The study reveals the need for implementing certain strategies in schools to enhance the student's performance with a good amount of emotional intelligence. School is a place where environment is created for students, to learn desirable behaviour. It is generally said that start with a child from where he is in other words anyone who is trying to create effective learning environment for his students should know the present status of them and should improve his students' study habits. The teachers should know the nature of his students.

Reference

- [1] Bai, S. (2011). Study of Anxiety Proneness and Emotional Intelligence in Relation to Academic Achievement of Pre-university Students. *Research Analysis and Evaluation*, 2(22): 1-5.
- [2] Chamundeswari, S. (2013). Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement among Students at the Higher Secondary Level. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(4), 178-18.
- [3] Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition, and Personality*, 9(3), 185-211. Steinberger, E. D. (1993). Improving student achievement. Virginia: American Association of School Administrators. Tiwari S.K, & Singh S. Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. *Education India Journal*, Vol. 6, Issue-2, May-2017. p.179-195.

REJUVENATING SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AND MENTAL WELLNESS THROUGH MINDFULNESS INSTUDENT-TEACHERS

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Abstract

Teaching is perceived as one of the greatest professions that brings transformation in the individual, society, nation, and the whole world as well. The teaching profession evolves with technical advancements, teaching methodologies, and teaching styles which the teachers have to update to survive in this competitive world. The majority of potential teachers find less time in performing their duties, planning the routine, handling situational stress, and executing and implementing their ideas in today's classroom. The heightened stress can induce mental health problems in teachers and reduce cognitive functioning. The inefficiency of professional training limits the teachers to challenge the world before them and may also turn them down in the teaching profession. Therefore, the paper aims to enhance the subjective well-being and mental health of the student-teachers through mindfulness which is incidental to coping with mental stress, improving healthy lifestyles, and enhancing working memory capacity and functional ability. The student teachers can refine their professional activities, renovate their inner well-being, perform duties with dedication and evaluate their strengths and professional standards. The more mindful the student teachers are, the more subjective well-being they will experience.

Keywords: *Subjective Well-Being, Mental Wellness, Mindfulness, Student Teachers.*

Introduction

In today's scenario, the profession of teaching is highly paced and highly competitive which may lead to being pressurized and developing psychological problems. Subjective well-being is defined as a person's cognitive and affective evaluations of his life. Anxiety can resist physical and mental functioning in teachers and as leaders of society, they must devise strategies to combat teacher burnout and develop a supportive environment. Hence student teachers must be trained to overcome the barriers of tomorrow's classroom by practicing mindfulness which culminates in better physical health. With a Buddhist-based background, mindfulness is considered an asset to improve the physiological and psychological health of the student teachers. Mindfulness has been associated with numerous aspects of well-being like improved attention, awareness or consciousness, socio-emotional regulation, and cognitive memory which are all related to subjective well-being thus enhancing the quality of life.

Literature Review

Mindfulness is an attention-related construct that refers to present-centered awareness and a nonjudgmental approach to the current moment (Kabat-Zinn, 1992). Extensive studies (Garland, Gaylord, & Park, 2009; Garland, Gaylord, & Fredrickson, 2011) have proposed that mindfulness is a resource that can help facilitate positive appraisal during the coping process. In addition, mindfulness-based practices help improve attention and lower cortisol levels, which is associated with stress (Tang et al., 2007; Danucalov et al., 2013). as well as improve other cognitive functions such as memory (Mrazek et al., 2013; Hölzel et al., 2013). Mindfulness has been effective in reducing stress associated with cancer (Carlson et al., 2001). Evidence-based research has demonstrated that mindfulness is effective across different populations such as veterans with posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (King et al., 2016), and various age groups such as young adults (Song & Lindquist, 2015), children (Mendelson et al., 2010; White, 2012), and adolescents (Barnes, Treiber, & Davis, 2001; Barnes, Bauza, & Treiber, 2003). Furthermore, prolonged mindfulness practice such as daily practice or through an 8-week intervention contributes to an increased ability to self-regulate automatic or habitual responses to stressful events. However, recently, Lim and Qu (2017) reported that a single session of mindfulness is also effective at enhancing attentional control. Cultivating Mindfulness – Ameliorating Positive outcomes in Student teachers. The positive effects of mindfulness have been witnessed in recent growing publications. The mounting stress levels have been resisted through mindfulness practices like mindful meditation by focusing on breathing, mindful wake-up, mindful eating, mindful listening, and staying focused on the present moment to bring about resilience in teachers. Some of the daily practices to bring more of mindfulness into your life are the following:-

1. Mindfulness meditation

It is a mental training practice that slows down your speedy thoughts, calms down your body and mind, pacifies negative thoughts, feelings, and sensations, and develops consciousness in the present moment. The first step is to sit in a comfortable position in your home with your head and back straight so that you do not feel distracted. If preferable we can have a timer that helps focus on meditation and avoid any excuses for having stopped meditating. One can meditate for longer sessions from 10 to 15 minutes or up to 30 minutes. One should focus on breathing paying attention to the body temperature by observing the warmth of the body when you exhale. There may be distracting thoughts that one need not suppress but let go of as just you see clouds passing by. Hence mindfulness meditation may develop positive impact and develop physical and mental immunity which builds resistance to illness.

2. Mindful Wake-up

The morning is crucial for setting the tone of the rest of the day so register your mind for the positive feelings you come across, try to plan thought-provoking conversations with your students, or send a short positive audio or video message to your friend or family. We rise every morning with innumerable thoughts thinking of the pending tasks that need completion or feeling the pressure of the day that has in store for us. Whatever may be the tasks wake up to tune your body with ease slowly and steadily. Don't rush up with the daily routine in the morning but feel relaxed to be thankful to god for having given you one more day of your life to enjoy the fullest. Try to secure positive actions for the rest of the day by asking yourself what is the motive of the day and transforming your creative ideas into action to develop a holistic personality.

3. Mindful Walking

Walking is an automatic process we often do every day but we hardly pay attention to the bodily sensations associated during walk. One can walk slowly with pace noticing the movements of your limb and other parts of your body. Ask yourself whether you feel light or heavy, relaxed or tensed and when your mind wanders bring back your sensations to the current context. Often choose a natural place walking barefoot in a peaceful surrounding sensing the sounds, voice, colors of nature, and smell around you. Hence mindful walking teaches one to be fully aware of the present moment which may prove beneficial to our student teachers if one practices it regularly in their life.

4. Mindful Eating

A student teacher has to be physically fit to carry out the activities of the day assigned to them. For this purpose, they have to be mindful of the things they eat in a day instead of getting sucked into hours of scrolling social media platforms. One has to boost their mental strength through mindful eating which ultimately boosts your immune and develops subjective well-being. Research has proved that when one eats with more mindfulness it helps digestion faster providing more minerals and vitamins to the body and boosting physical and mental wellness.

5. Mindful listening

Often we end up observed in our thoughts failing to hear what others speak or respond to them when solutions are demanded. When you are in a conversation, pierce your ears to what others are conveying paying full attention to the context specified. This enhances the quality of listening thereby changing your quality of conversation with others.

6. Observing your Emotions and senses

Emotions always advance when one pays attention to past sensations or feelings. Don't try to subdue your emotions or overcome them without responding to them. Create awareness about your emotions and seek out solutions to undo them without disabling the inner mind. Explore various ideas to sort out problems as it comes and create the space for your experiences of the emotion undergone to assist you in building the strength of that particular emotion exhibited.

Benefits of Mindfulness

Mindfulness brings a sense of meaningfulness to the most mundane daily tasks. It allows us to enjoy the very essence of life by making us engage with the things we do regularly and observing the surroundings without any distractions. It helps to pay attention to our senses and emotions, experiencing every moment of the day with complete enjoyment and bringing consistency to our routine and daily tasks with daily practice. Bringing mindfulness into your routine will help develop awareness, attention, and subjective well-being in the student teachers. It builds immunity in the person tackling stress and avoids any ailments or illnesses in any individual. The longer you practice mindfulness, the greater the benefits one can derive from it like self-control, objectivity, enhanced flexibility, improved concentration, and mental clarity.

Other Benefits Include

- 1) Improving cognitive ability
- 2) Slowing brain aging
- 3) Reducing stress, anxiety, and depression symptoms
- 4) Increasing a sense of well-being
- 5) Helping with pain management
- 6) Improving quality of life for those living with chronic conditions

Conclusion

Research studies have proved greater benefits from integrating mindfulness into an individual's life. Mindfulness meditation has been shown to reduce anxiety and depression in educated populations also creating a positive impact on one's life. With greater awareness through mindfulness meditation, mindful wake-up, mindful senses and mindful listening, we make better choices, make quality conversations, build stronger relationships, and remain calm throughout every ups and downs of our life.

References

- [1] 1.Amutio, A., Franco, C., Pérez-Fuentes, M. C., Gázquez, J. J., and Mercader, I. (2015). Mindfulness training for reducing anxiety, and depression in fibromyalgia patients. *Front. Psychol.* 5:1572. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01572
- [2] Baer R.A. Self-focused attention and mechanisms of change in mindfulness-based treatment. *Cogn. Behav. Ther.* 2009;38:15–20. doi: 10.1080/16506070902980703.
- [3] Brown K.W., Ryan R.M. The benefits of being present: Mindfulness and its role in psychological well-being. *J. Personal. Soc. Psychol.* 2003;84:822–848. doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.84.4.822.
- [4] Brown, K. W., Creswell, J. D., and Ryan, R. M. (2015). "The evolution of mindfulness research," in *Handbook of Mindfulness: Theory, Research, and Practice*, eds K. W. Brown, J. D. Creswell, and R. M. Ryan, (New York, NY: Guilford), 13–19.
- [5] Carmody, J., and Baer, R. A. (2008). Relationships between mindfulness practice and levels of mindfulness, medical and psychological symptoms and well-being in a mindfulness-based stress reduction program. *J. Behav. Med.* 31, 23–33. doi: 10.1007/s10865-007-9130-7
- [6] 6.Davis, M. C., Zautra, A. J., Wolf, L. D., Tennen, H., and Yeung, E. W. (2015). Mindfulness and cognitive-behavioral interventions for chronic pain: differential effects on daily pain reactivity and stress reactivity. *J. Consult. Clin. Psychol.* 83, 24–35. doi: 10.1037/a0038200
- [7] 7.Germer C., Neff K. *Teaching the Mindful Self-Compassion Program: A Guide for Professionals*. Guilford Press; New York, NY, USA: 2019.
- [8] Gu J., Strauss C., Bond R., Cavanagh K. How do mindfulness-based cognitive therapy and mindfulness-based stress reduction improve mental health and wellbeing? A systematic review and meta-analysis of mediation studies. *Clin. Psychol. Rev.* 2015;37:1–12. doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2015.01.006.
- [9] Hanley A., Warner A., Garland E.L. Associations between mindfulness, psychological well-being, and subjective well-being with respect to contemplative practice. *J. Happiness Stud.* 2015;16:1423–1436. doi: 10.1007/s10902-014-9569-5.
- [10] Hervás, G., Cebolla, A., and Soler, J. (2016). Mindfulness-based psychological interventions and benefits: state of the art. *Clín. Salud.* 27, 115–124. doi: 10.1016/j.clysa.2016.09.002
- [11] Johnson, Anita, "Mindfulness Practices Used During Crisis Leadership Reported by Minnesota Secondary School Administrators" (2022). *Culminating Projects in Education Administration and Leadership*. 91.
- [12] Shapiro S.L., Carlson L.E., Astin J.A., Freedman B. Mechanisms of mindfulness. *J. Clin. Psychol.* 2006;62:373–386. doi: 10.1002/jclp.20237.
- [13] Teal C., Downey L.A., Lomas J.E., Ford T.C., Bunnett E.R., Stough C. The Role of Dispositional Mindfulness and Emotional Intelligence in Adolescent Males. *Mindfulness.* 2019;10:159–167. doi: 10.1007/s12671-018-0962-8.

WOMEN'S LEGAL RIGHTS IN PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS: A MULTICULTURAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This research examined the women's legal rights in prospective teachers: a multicultural perspective. The primary target of this review is to discover the familiarity with lawful rights and in planned educators. For the present study, the researchers used a normative survey method. A sample of 284 prospective teachers was selected by random sampling technique. Women's legal rights questionnaire developed and validated by the researcher was used in the study. For the analysis of data, the descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation and 't' test were employed. The findings revealed significant difference in women's legal rights prospective teachers with respect to marital status.

Keywords: *Legal rights, multicultural perspective and prospective teachers*

Introduction

Multiculturalism is the process of providing equal justice to all religions and people of different cultures, without regard for race or culture. (Multiculturalism in Education, 2021.) In contrast to monoculturalism, multiculturalism, according to Banks (2008), is a multifaceted notion that requires respecting different cultural features such as age, sexual orientation, handicap, social class, ethnicity, religion, and language. Teachers' good attitudes toward multicultural education are critical variables in developing an acceptable classroom environment in which all children can obtain equal education without being subjected to discrimination (Banks, 1994). Pre-service education is useful in creating prospective teachers' attitudes and tendencies toward multicultural education in terms of establishing this knowledge of education.

Legal Rights for Women

A person's right is defined as any action permitted by law. Legal rights are the rights granted by the government to people of a country to enjoy certain freedoms. Every citizen is affected by these rights. Except for the law itself, there is no recourse for violations of these. Legal rights differ from moral rights, natural rights, and even fundamental rights. For example, the right to vote and the right to sue. Several laws empower women to overcome adversities such as discrimination, harassment, violence, and abuse. Women have been subjected to mental harassment, physical torment, and sexual violence since time immemorial. And violations of women's rights continue to be rampant in India and throughout the world. However, things do not have to remain as they have. Women's injustice can be effectively contested – legally, if not socially. Women's rights can be divided into two basic categories: constitutional rights and legal rights. Those guaranteed by the Constitution include the right to equality, non-discrimination in employment on the basis of gender, the right to appropriate means of subsistence, equal pay for equal effort, equitable and humane working conditions, and maternity leave, among others. Legal rights, on the other hand, are available to women through the country's prevailing laws or enactments.

Review of Literature

Shankar DasharathDunghav(2021), examined Multicultural curriculum, multicultural learning teaching methods, equality in classroom teaching and the development of mutual cultural tolerance are all critical for the country's future education system and development. Murat Debbag et.al (2020), study on although this transformation occurs in theory, teachers' managerial behaviors, communication styles, and prejudices are influenced by their attitudes and beliefs throughout classroom practice. Ayub Mallick(2013), it has occasionally been possible for multiple political parties (multiethnic) to work together, create coalitions after elections and even before, and reach compromises on contentious issues impacting cultural and group rights. Bikashita Choudhury(2016) Human rights that have been designed with conventional society in mind may not be well equipped to accommodate these rights.

Need and Significance of the Study

Every educated people have no much knowledge of the legal rights, especially women do not practice the legal rights in their life situation. So, this study is very essential to get an women's legal rights of prospective teachers for multicultural perspective. The study is considered as an important one to develop the

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thorough knowledge of legal rights. To make a great women's society and free from women's against problem in their life surroundings.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 2) To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 3) To find out whether there is any significant difference between married and unmarried prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 4) To find out whether there is any significant difference between prospective teachers whose parents are educated and uneducated in their women's legal rights.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) There is no significant difference between male and female prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 2) There is no significant difference between rural and urban prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 3) There is no significant difference between married and unmarried prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.
- 4) There is no significant difference between prospective teachers whose parents are literate and illiterate in their women's legal rights.

Methodology

Generally research problems have different methods for investigation. The method followed in the present study is normative survey method. Sample: For the present study the investigators collected the samples from the prospective teachers from colleges in karaikudi area. The investigators collected a sample of 284 prospective teachers from different B.Ed colleges in Karaikudi. Adequate representations were given to factors like gender, locality, marital status and parents' educational level. Tool used in the study: Tools for collecting the pertinent data, the investigators used women's legal rights Questionnaire which was developed and validated by the investigators and field experts.

Data Analysis

The collected data for the variables are analysed by using 't' test.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.

Table 1 Difference in the women's legal rights of Prospective Teachers with respect to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
Male	16	171.38	33.39	0.602	NS
Female	268	167.05	27.57		

(At 5% level of significance table value of 't' is 1.96)

The calculated 't' value (0.602) is lesser than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis is accepted and so it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the women's legal rights of prospective teachers with respect to gender.

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Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between rural and urban prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.

Table 2 Difference in the women's legal rights of Prospective Teachers with respect to Locality

Locality	N	Mean	SD	Calculated value 't'	Remarks at 5% level
Rural	229	166.44	26.095	1.055	NS
Urban	55	170.85	34.391		

(At 5% level of significance table value of 't' is 1.96)

The calculated 't' value (1.055) is lesser than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis is accepted and so it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the women's legal rights of prospective teachers with respect to locality.

Null Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between married and unmarried prospective teachers in their women's legal rights.

Table 3 Difference in the women's legal rights of Prospective Teachers with respect to marital status

Marital status	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
Married	103	171.34	29.352	2.052	S
Unmarried	180	185.04	24.593		

(At 5% level of significance table value of 't' is 1.96)

The calculated 't' value (2.052) is lesser than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis is rejected and so it is concluded that there is significant difference in the women's legal rights of prospective teachers with respect to marital status.

Null Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between prospective teachers whose parents are literate and illiterate in their women's legal rights.

Table 4 Difference in the women's legal rights of Prospective Teachers with respect to parents education level.

Parents Education Level	N	Mean	SD	Calculated Value 't'	Remarks at 5% level
Literate	157	165.22	28.321	1.428	NS
Illiterate	126	169.98	27.296		

(At 5% level of significance table value of 't' is 1.96)

The calculated 't' value (1.428) is lesser than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis is accepted and so it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the women's legal rights of prospective teachers with respect to parent's education level.

Discussion

The recent multicultural education advances in the field of education have made women's legal rights a vital competency for the present day prospective teachers. In this study, the result reveals that unmarried prospective teachers have high-women's legal rights compared to married prospective teachers in karaikudi area. This may be due to the reasons that have more attitude and knowledge in women's legal rights. From the findings, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between male and female and rural and urban

and literate and illiterate in their women's legal rights in multicultural education perspective.

Conclusion

At present although women's legal rights and law knowledge are multicultural education essential requirement for prospective teachers. They are becoming increasingly important as a result of factors such as limited access to current books and journals and difficulty obtaining up-to-date information, which may affect exam performance and work after graduation. The present study contributes to the women's legal rights in prospective teachers for multicultural perspective in around Karaikudi. The factors identified during the present study could be used to improve legal rights amongst.

References

- [1] ASLAN, S. (2022). The Effect of Prospective Teachers' Beliefs About the Necessity of Multicultural Education and Self-Efficacy Perceptions of Multicultural Education: A Path Model. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 9(1), 102–114. <https://doi.org/10.52380/ijpes.2022.9.1.552>
- [2] A Study of Legal Awareness among Women in the Areas of Marriage. (n.d.).
- [3] Das, R. (2015). A comparative study on the level of awareness about constitutional and legal rights among working and Non-working women of Kokrajhar town. 3(10), 14–19.
- [4] Kellogg, L. D. (n.d.). States and Multicultural Education Policies: An Event History States and Multicultural Education Policies: An Event History Analysis Analysis Repository Citation Repository Citation. <https://doi.org/10.34917/7777312>
- [5] Khound, R. (2019). Minority Rights In Indian Democracy: A Multicultural Perspective.
- [6] INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH, 8(10).
- [7] www.ijstr.org
- [8] Legal Awareness about Women Rights: The Indian Adolescent. (2021). *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(02). <https://doi.org/10.47750/cibg.2021.27.02.164>
- [9] Mallick, M. A. (n.d.). Multiculturalism, Minority Rights and Democracy in India. In *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS (Vol. 16, Issue 1))*. www.Iosrjournals.Org
- [10] Mlinar, K., & Krammer, G. (2021). Multicultural attitudes of prospective teachers: The influence of multicultural ideology and national pride. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 84, 107–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2021.07.008>
- [11] MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION. (n.d.). http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Affirmative_action
- [12] Multicultural Education in Indian Context Rashibha Baghel 4 articles Follow. (2022). https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/multicultural-education-indian-context-rashibha-baghel/?trk=articles_directory
- [13] Parry, A. B. (2021). INDIAN MULTICULTURALISM IN PRACTICE. *Indian Politics and Law Review Journal*, 06, 310–354. <https://doi.org/10.55662/iplr.2021.601>
- [14] Law Review Journal, 06, 310–354. <https://doi.org/10.55662/iplr.2021.601>
- [15] Perkins, & Rotha M. (n.d.). THE MULTICULTURAL AWARENESS, KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS AND ATTITUDES OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS: A QUANTITATIVE.
- [16] Shambhunath, B. (2016). Awareness on legal rights of women : A study of Kalaburagidistrict. 12–16.
- [17] Sharma, M. (2021). Multicultural Education in India: Opportunities and Challenges. In *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM) (Vol. 9, Issue 9)*.
- [18] Singh, A. K., & Raza, M. A. (n.d.). Multicultural Education in Secondary School: Issues and Challenges in Indian Context. *Journal of Socio-Educational & Cultural Research*, 2(5).
- [19] THE INCLUSION OF MULTICULTURALISM IN SCHOOL EDUCATION: A STUDY OF THE POLICIES AND PRACTICES.

A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE RAMIFICATIONS OF HOLISTIC MEDICAL SCIENCE OF HOMEOPATHY

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Abstract

Conventional medical professional education encounters routine difficulties due to, the complexity and variability of the human body and disease processes, the time and expenses involved in conducting large-scale clinical trials and limitations of current diagnostic tools and treatments. The additional challenges of balancing the needs of the patient with the need for scientific research. Homoeopathy is a Holistic medical science approved and recognized by the Government of India under the Ministry of AYUSH. A curriculum for any medical science typically focus on the diagnosis and treatment of diseases. While a curriculum for holistic medical science places greater emphasis on patient-centered care, which takes into account the patient's needs, concerns, and preferences, and seeks to address the whole person, not just their symptoms. This becomes challenging to isolate the specific effects of a holistic practice and to provide a clear evidence of its efficacy. The complexity of holistic medicine and its multi-faceted interventions make it challenging to establish evidence on a cellular level. A curriculum for holistic medical science is required to adopt an interdisciplinary approach, which draws on various disciplines such as psychology, sociology, and environmental studies, to understand the impact of social, cultural, and environmental factors on health. The initiative taken by the National Commission of Homoeopathy to redesign the curriculum of under graduate and postgraduate courses of Homoeopathy aims at having profound research based knowledge of Homoeopathy with contemporary and technological advancement and extensive practical training, thereby attempting to overcome the challenges of Holistic medical education.

Keywords: *Holistic Medical Education, Homoeopathy, Curriculum, National Commission of Homoeopathy*

Introduction

Primary aim of any professional education is to focus on preparing students for professional careers that require a specific set of knowledge and skills. It typically includes classroom instruction and theoretical learning, as well as practical experience and internships. The high cost of tuition and student debt is a major setback to medical education in India. The limited access to professional education in rural or underserved areas; to find and maintain clinical or practical experience results in limited opportunities for hands-on experience and training during professional education, only add to the adversities. The study of human body engulfs complexity and variability of the disease processes which has to match with the development and the availability of current diagnostic tools and treatments. The pedagogy of medical education in India had traditionally focused on the didactic method, which emphasizes lectures, memorization, and the learning of facts, until recent years. However, there has been a shift towards more student-centered and problem-based learning (PBL) approaches. This change is driven by the recognition that the traditional didactic method may not be sufficient to prepare medical students for the complex and rapidly changing field of healthcare. The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined health, as "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity."

Suffice to say that health is a complex concept, which cannot be solely determined by biological values and levels or the exhibition of cellular disease. Health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being, and it encompasses various dimensions such as physical, emotional, psychological, and social well-being. Biological values and levels, such as blood pressure or cholesterol levels, are important indicators of physical health, but they do not fully capture the complexity of health. For example, a person may have normal blood pressure and biological values, but still experience mental health issues such as depression or anxiety. With this, we can conclude that man is not merely a human body with a collection of tissues and mass, but an entity beyond the cellular existence. The closest approach to treat an individual having the perspective such as stated by WHO is achieved only by a Holistic medicine. Holistic medicine is an approach to health and wellness that considers the whole person - body, mind, spirit, and emotions - in the quest for optimal health and wellness. It emphasizes the connection between the physical, emotional, and spiritual aspects of a person, and recognizes that all of these aspects must be in balance for a person to be truly healthy. However, this makes it immeasurable in identifying the cellular and organic pathway of medicinal action. The cost of medication by Homoeopathic medicines is very low and mostly the people who approach Homoeopathic physicians are those wanting to avoid surgical interventions or those who are tired of taking conventional medications without relief and or those who cannot afford the hospital and allopathic expenses. Homeopathy is a Holistic system of alternative medicine developed in the late 18th century by a German

physician named Dr. Samuel Hahnemann.

One of the fundamental laws of Homoeopathy is the Law of Similars. According to this law, a drug capable of producing in a healthy person a diseased-state exactly similar to that observed in a diseased person, acts as a curative agent if the disease is in a curable stage. In the incurable stage of the disease, however, the same drug acts as the best palliative. The very foundation of homoeopathic practice considers man not only as an individual, but also as a complete unit in himself, of which all his parts comprise a well-balanced whole. Homoeopathy, therefore, does not consider any one part as being ill, but considers the manifestation of illness in one part in its relation to the whole man. The National Commission of Homoeopathy (NCH), which has been constituted by an act of parliament known as NCH Act, 2020 and which came into force on 05.07.2021 by gazette notification dated 05.07.2021 governs and regulates the curriculum of Graduate and Post Graduate Degree courses in Homoeopathy in India. Today Homoeopathy as Holistic medicine faces the challenge to gather scientific evidence while aiming to address the body, mind, spirit, and emotions, as these practices often involve complex and multi-faceted interventions. However, in the contemporary world the only way of acceptance of Holistic medicine relies totally on evidence-based research.

Some of the fallacies in Homoeopathic education, which brought ambiguity to its system, were-

- 1) Lack of standardization: Homoeopathic education is not standardized across India and in different institutions, which can lead to confusion and inconsistencies in the training provided to students.
- 2) Limited research: There is limited Qualitative research on the effectiveness of homoeopathic treatments, which is making it difficult to establish itself a scientific medical stream.
- 3) Limited clinical experience: Lack of clinical exposure and teaching may not provide students with enough clinical experience, which can make it difficult for students to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations.
- 4) Quality control: There are no strict regulations and guidelines in place to ensure the quality of homoeopathic education and practice. This can lead to the provision of inconsistent and substandard education and treatments.
- 5) Limited Funding: Homoeopathic education may not receive the same level of funding as conventional medical education, which can make it difficult for institutions to provide students with the resources and facilities they need to learn effectively.

To establish Homoeopathy as an authentic scientific system of medicine the National Council of Homoeopathy has re-designed the entire Homoeopathic curriculum that will be soon official and implemented. The prepared curriculum fulfils all the necessities of an ideal Homoeopathic Curriculum that will make it compete with the contemporary medical educational system and correct the ramifications of Holistic medical science of Homoeopathy and its pedagogy. An ideal curriculum required today for Homoeopathy at the graduate and postgraduate levels in India should lay stress on following issues, along with having profound knowledge of Homoeopathy in -

- 1) Clinical training: Students should have hands-on clinical experience in the diagnosis and treatment of patients through supervised clinical training in Homoeopathic clinics and hospitals.
- 2) Pharmacology and toxicology: Students should not only learn about the use of Homoeopathic remedies, but also their potential interactions with other medications.
- 3) Research and evidence-based practice: Students should be exposed to the latest research and evidence-based practices in Homoeopathy and be encouraged to conduct their own research.
- 4) Interdisciplinary education: Students should learn to collaborate and communicate effectively with other healthcare systems to provide comprehensive and coordinated care.
- 5) Introduction to other complementary and alternative medicine systems: Students should be introduced to other alternative medicine systems and their principles.
- 6) Ethics and professionalism: Students should learn about the ethical principles and responsibilities of a Homoeopathic practitioner, including patient confidentiality and informed consent.

Summary

In summary, Health is a complex concept that encompasses various dimensions of physical, emotional, psychological, and social well-being. Biological values and levels or the exhibition of cellular disease does not solely determine Health of a person. Similarly, the exhibition of cellular disease does not vouch for the person's overall well-being. The conventional medical system involves the generation of data in quantitative form, which is subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis in a formal and rigid fashion. Not restricting there, they consider that only the Quantitative research is the research to be considered and is the only scientific research. This marks the biggest challenge for a system like Homoeopathy, as Qualitative and

Quantitative research being two opposite banks of the river.

Conclusion

The integration of technology in medical education should be encouraged and pursued. This includes the use of e-learning, virtual patients, and telemedicine, which can enhance the learning experience, and make medical education more accessible and cost-effective. Research plays an important role in medical professional education, by providing students with the knowledge, skills, and critical thinking abilities needed to make evidence-based decisions in their future practice as healthcare professionals. Integrating evidence-based research in Homoeopathic education will bring back the glory of the system, which is losing due to its inability to prove itself at the cellular level and in Quantitative measure.

References

- [1] Vocational training in India: determinants of participation and effect on wages Authors: - Rishi Kumar^{1*}, Shravanth Mandava¹ and Venkata Sandeep Gopanapalli² Kumar et al. *Empirical Res Voc Ed Train*(2019) 11:3 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-019-0078-y>
- [2] Institute of Medicine (US) Forum on Drug Discovery, Development, and Translation. *Transforming Clinical Research in the United States: Challenges and Opportunities: Workshop Summary*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2010. 3, Challenges in Clinical Research. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK50888/>
- [3] Cite as: *Int J High Dilution Res*. 2022; 21(CF): 01-03 1 <https://doi.org/10.51910/ijhdr.v21icf.1141>
- [4] Gloria L. Krahn, Ann Robinson, Alexa J. Murray, Susan M. Havercamp, Susan Havercamp, Rebecca Andridge, L. Eugene Arnold, Jarrett Barnhill, Shawn Bodle, Ethan Boerner, Alixe Bonardi, Mary Lou Bourne, Christine Brown, Andrew Buck, Sarah Burkett, Richard Chapman, Chelsea Cobranchi, Christopher Cole, Dan Davies, Travis Dresbach, Jeanne Farr, Mary Lee Fay, Robert Fletcher, Braden Gertz, Jill Hollway, Margo Izzo, Gloria Krahn, Rosie Lawrence-Slater, Luc Lecavalier, Alexa Murray, Kristin Page, Samantha Perry, Ashley Poling, Paula Rabidoux, Robert Rice, Ann Robinson, Margaret Rosencrans, Megan Ryan, Christopher Sanford, Colin Schaeffer, John Seeley, Karrie Shogren, Kristy Stepp, Marci Straughter, Lara Sucheston-Campbell, Marc J. Tassé, Christopher Taylor, Katherine Walton, Michael Wehmeyer, Craig Williams, Andrea Witwer, It's time to reconsider how we define health: Perspective from disability and chronic condition, *Disability and Health Journal*, Volume 14, Issue 4, 2021, 101129, ISSN 1936-6574, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2021.101129>.
- [5] Chenhao Hu, Ke Zhu, Kun Huang, Bo Yu, Wenchen Jiang, Kaiping Peng, Fei Wang, Using natural intervention to promote subjective well-being of essential workers during public-health crises: A Study during COVID-19 pandemic, *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Volume 79, 2022, 101745, ISSN 0272-4944, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101745>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272494421001985>) Abstract: Essential workers such as medical workers and pol
- [6] Dr. Tilottama B Galande, Challenges for research in Homoeopathy, *MULTIDISCIPLINARY SUBJECTS FOR RESEARCH V Vol 2* (Edited Book Chapter), March 2021, ISBN 979-8-718-87982-7, RED'SHINE PUBLICATION INC.
- [7] [http://nch.org.in/upload/HomoeopathyGraduateDegree%20Course%E2%80%9393BachelorofHomoeopathicMedicineandSurgery\(B.H.M.S\)Regulations-2022.pdf](http://nch.org.in/upload/HomoeopathyGraduateDegree%20Course%E2%80%9393BachelorofHomoeopathicMedicineandSurgery(B.H.M.S)Regulations-2022.pdf)

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HOLISTIC HEALTH AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

"Health is a state of body. Wellness is a state of being" - **Stanford**

Today's schools face difficulties in terms of preparing students for the demands of life in the context of the research title. Critical thinking, creativity, cooperation and creativity and reading, writing or arithmetic know how are no longer able to satisfy the demands of the learner in the 21st century. The classrooms in today's schools are beset with a variety of issues, including but not limited to: indiscipline or bullying issues; a lack of student motivation or drive; irregularity; the absence of parental support; an excessive obsession with tech-gadgets; moving on to depression and suicidal tendencies; etc. Not only this, but also the fact that the modern workplace needs a rising amount of flexibility, creativity, social intelligence, and other soft skills which makes the schools impossible to ignore its importance as necessary aspects while preparing children for life. Even while parents now look to schools for help in a wider variety of areas, the typical amount of time a kid spends in school has remained the same. This is despite the fact that the demands placed on schools have grown. The pursuit of health, personal development, and a higher quality of life should be incorporated into the curriculum of schools, and children should be instructed on how to live a life that is balanced. This is a growing necessity.

Keywords: *Healthy Students, Physical Education, Holistic Health, Success, Well-Being*

Introduction

"A healthy lifestyle is the bedrock for all other success. When our kids are healthy, they achieve"

- **Kevin Corrinet**

Students need to learn how to take care of their minds, bodies, and spirits in order to reach a state of equilibrium. If one of these three aspects is constantly neglected or ignored, our health will not be at its best, and we will not be able to reach our full potential. A sustainable condition of positive mood and attitude, resilience, and contentment with oneself, one's relationships, and one's experiences at school can be thought of as well-being. Rather, the student's physical growth, social development, emotional development, moral development, spiritual development, and artistic development are all essential components of a student's overall "well-being." Every morning when teachers arrive at school, they make an effort to improve health and wellness of the students to the fullest possible extent so that they may produce quality work, live long, full, and healthy lives. Living a life that is well- balanced is essential for anybody who wants to have a healthy childhood, a happy adulthood, and an enhanced overall quality of life. If students could take care of certain factors that influence state of wellness, such as nutrition, physical activity, stress-coping methods, good relationships, and career orientation, their success rate in life would be higher. These factors include good nutrition, physical activity, stress-coping methods, good relationships, and career orientation.

The provision of free and equal access to early childhood education and care, as well as to elementary and secondary education, is a crucial component of an effective educational system. According to the World Health Organization's (WHO) definition of health, the so- called "determinants of population health" (also written as "determinants of population health") can be seen as assets for wellbeing. When we talk about assets, we're referring to the fact that having particular attributes increases the possibility of having a higher degree of wellbeing. The curve representing population growth is moved to the right when efforts are concentrated on the entire community or population. This guarantees that a higher number of individuals benefit from improved health and well-being, and that there is an increase in the proportion of children whose health and well-being outcomes fall within the average or above average range.

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The majority of today's schools include P.E. as an essential part of their overall curriculum. Because it is necessary to create the basis of a sound mind in a sound body, the curriculum includes a significant amount of time devoted to sports and games. According to the UNESCO International Charter of Physical Education and Sport from 1978, "Every human being has a fundamental right of access to physical education and sport," both of which are vital for the whole development of a person's personality. Since then, a significant amount of focus has been placed on ensuring that physical education and sports are fundamental components of the curriculum. But there are some schools that do not properly encourage students to participate in sporting events, and some parents add to the physical hindrance by not believing that this field can bring as many or even better chances of success than the academic field. Once the student has been identified as a national achiever due to his advanced training needs and infrastructural requirement, the state is required to take action in order to provide high quality development of effective physical training instructors.

Those of us who engage in regular physical activity do so in part because we want to enhance our overall level of health, both now and in the future. We work hard to achieve the highest possible level of health and happiness. When we make changes to the way we live, our overall health also improves, and we have fewer instances of illness and disease. If you ask the majority of people what it means to be healthy, you will typically get a response that includes the four aspects of fitness that were discussed before (cardio respiratory ability, muscular ability, flexibility, and body composition). According to research conducted by scientists, an individual should engage in at least sixty minutes worth of physical exercise on a daily basis in order to maintain or improve their health.

These are the Recommendations that have been Made

Endurance: Perform continuous movement that is beneficial to your heart, lungs, and circulatory system on four to seven days each week. The amount of time needed for improvements is proportional to the work put in. **Flexibility:** Flexibility requires that you exercise light reaching, bending, and stretching anywhere from four to seven days per week in order to maintain relaxed muscles and movable joints. **Strength:** Work on your strength by doing resistance exercises twice to four times a week to improve your posture and build your muscles and bones.

Physical Activity

- 1) Protects against or helps students to manage the majority of chronic disorders in future (for example, diabetes and heart disease).
- 2) Allows students to operate autonomously, which allows them to have pleasure in their lives and experience growth.
- 3) It makes it possible after being parents to continue to participate in the busy lives of their children, grandkids, and the communities in which they reside.

According to the findings of a recent study, the proportion of the world's population that is underweight has decreased since 1975, but the proportion that is fat has climbed. In 1975, 13.8% males and 14.6% women were underweight. In 2014, these percentages were down to 8.8% for males and 9.7% for women respectively. In 1975, the percentage of obese males was just 3.2% and the percentage of obese women was only 6.4%; however, by 2014, those percentages had climbed to 10.8% and 14.9%, respectively. In the 21st century, morbid obesity has reached epidemic proportions in India, where it currently affects 5% of the population. India's obesity problem has reached epidemic proportions in this century. The rate of obesity in India is rising, mirroring the trajectory seen in a number of other emerging countries.

Holistic Health

Ayurveda is a discipline that has been around for more than 5,000 years and has been used to improve wellbeing in India. Ayurveda is derived from the Sanskrit words Ayurs (life) and Veda (knowledge), and it is a branch of the Hindu scriptures known as the Vedas. Ayurveda has had an impact on Buddhist philosophy as well as Eastern and Western approaches to health care, and it is also beginning to find a place in contemporary dietary trends. Ayurveda is revered by those who practise it as a sacred medical system because it brings together natural ingredients, spirituality, and food. In a nutshell, the sustenance of the mind and the spirit are inextricably linked to the feeding of the body. Student's physical well-being is just one component of their whole state of health.

The following are some of the other aspects of health that, in addition to physical wellbeing, are equally essential to a healthy life

Wellness in Society

The capacity to engage successfully with other people and the surrounding environment, as well as to form personally meaningful connections. A structured curriculum in our schools also helps children improve

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their capacity to relate to and interact with other students, instructors, and members of the communities they attend school in. Beginning with play school and continuing through high school, children have access to the support of counsellors and special educators at their schools, who are there to observe and assist them as they develop into healthy adults who respect the genders, religions, and communities of other parts of the world. It is a well-established truth that a significant factor in determining a person's level of social wellness is their capacity to form and sustain healthy connections with members of their family, social circle, and workplace. Volunteer work and being a member of a community or social group are two examples of the kinds of day-to-day activities that contribute to an individual's sense of social welfare and help the community as well as the surrounding environment. Acceptance in social groups is vital for helping students manage stress and the negative effects of stressful life events and circumstances since it leads to a greater feeling of well-being.

The State of One's Mind

It is the capacity for intellectual growth and development via learning. Enhancing one's mental health can be accomplished through a combination of life events and more formal organisations (like education). Both a personal dedication to studying over one's whole life and a desire in imparting one's expertise to others are necessary components of intellectual wellbeing. Intellectual health may assist with positive thinking and decision-making, as well as provide an individual the ability to apply innovative problem-solving strategies to overcome obstacles and challenges. "The degree to which one engages in creative and stimulating activities, as well as the use of resources to increase knowledge and focus on the acquisition, development, application, and articulation of critical thinking," is what it means to have "critical thinking". As a result, education and literacy are essential components to accomplishing intellectual wellbeing, and it is generally accepted that these factors have an effect on an individual's health and well-being since they make it possible to develop coping strategies and other life skills. Education and literacy have been found to have a substantial association with future personal wealth and well-being. They can also aid with the capacity to operate in a variety of societal circumstances, as well as plan for and adapt to future events.

Wellness of the Spirits

It is the capacity to exert control over one's feelings to the point that one is not only able to adequately express them but also feels comfortable doing so. The state of one's mental and emotional health may be measured by how they feel about themselves, their relationships, their objectives, and their personal strengths. It takes into account factors like as contentment with one's life and a sound mental state. "Having a sense of individual vitality, opportunities to undertake meaningful, engaging activities that confer feelings of competence and autonomy, and the possession of a stock of inner resources that helps one cope when things go wrong" are all components of happiness, according to the definition given by psychologists. The sensation of happiness can also assist in the healing process for those who are unwell, and it can serve as a barrier to illness for those who are otherwise healthy. It has been shown that having a sense of control over at least some aspects of one's life and the capacity to successfully manage the pressures and challenges that are an inevitable part of living a normal life can have a beneficial impact on one's overall health and well-being. Psychological wellness encompasses both of these aspects. Incorporating activities such as circle time or one-on-one counselling for behaviour management or career mapping are very much a part and parcel of any decent school's yearly plan these days. Value education and the imparting of life skills are a vital element of the curriculum at every school.

Healing on a Spiritual Level

A faith in a unifying power or principle. It is the capacity to build peace and harmony in our lives, and while it differs from person to person, at its centre lays the idea of faith. The capacity to bring about coherence between one's ideals and one's actions, as well as the awareness of a shared goal that serves to connect creation together. In addition to that, it serves as a helpful reminder to the kids that this time is specifically reserved for them, and that by engaging in this activity, they are contributing to their overall health and well-being. Students may only gain the skill of being with themselves via their schooling, whether it be through the daily morning prayers that are held in the majority of schools, through meditation and yogic exercises, by keeping quiet, or through going on nature walks. Both the achievement of educational accomplishment and the maintenance of one's physical and mental health are essential to one's quality of life. Education does have an effect on health through a variety of different complicated pathways, some of which include income, access to health care, and improved work possibilities. What schools should keep doing is the following:

- 1) To cultivate an atmosphere that places a premium on one's physical health, mental health, and general wellbeing as a basis for achieving success and enjoyment throughout one's whole life.
- 2) To create physical places for activities such as exercise, recreation, and athletics, as well as

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mindfulness, spirituality, and reflective practices; to foster meaningful social engagement; and to foster reflection on one's experiences.

- 3) The goal of this project is to create a space that is a destination for students and that is dedicated to promoting holistic well-being through the expert delivery of a variety of services, such as health services, counselling and psychological services, and other programmes like workshops and seminars.
- 4) To provide meal alternatives that are better for your health while expanding the traditional dining spaces' potential as communal and participatory settings.
- 5) Investigate in a methodical manner different methods to make the academic setting less stressful than it has to be and to encourage a healthy balance between work and personal life.

It is possible for service providers to have a better understanding of the most effective methods to offer services, maximise engagement, and enhance results with the help of the experiences and expertise of children, young people, families, members of the community, and local groups. Before joining the workforce with any degree of success, the vast majority of students first finish their primary and secondary education and then pursue higher education or training. Some of them require additional assistance in order to effectively complete their studies and then go on to the next stage of their education or training. The majority of these young people can receive the assistance they need through student support services, school-based health and well-being personnel, mentors, the community, or businesses in the area. India is in severe need of a comprehensive health care system in order to serve its population, the most of which are unable to even afford the most fundamental level of medical attention. When services, education, families, and the community work together effectively to form partnerships, it will be easier to establish a common commitment and collaborate on measures that will enhance health and well-being results. Therefore, a world with holistic well-being that satisfies the demands of hunger, love, and health is not an unattainable fantasy but rather a reality that can be achieved at an inexpensive cost.

References

- [1] <https://www.oakridge.in/gachibowli/blogs/physical-education-and-its-importance-in-holistic-learning/>
- [2] <https://www.jliedu.com/blog/physical-education-public-health/>
- [3] <https://comorbidityguidelines.org.au/what-is-a-holistic-health-care-framework/physical-activity-1>
- [4] <https://www.canberra.edu.au/unit/9873/1/2021>
- [5] ercircle.in/engage/career/career/holistic-education-how-does-pe-contribute-to-the-overall-development-of-the-child-845.html
- [6] <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16870506/>
- [7] https://oshwiki.eu/wiki/Daily_physical_education_as_part_of_holistic_health_promotion_in_Hungarian_schools
- [8] <https://www.ipl.org/essay/Active-Learning-Approach-FCLAFFN4FU>

IMPACT OF PHYSICAL VARIABLES AMONG OB ESE WOMEN DUE TO THE APPLICATION OF SELECTED PILATES AND CALISTHENICS EXERCISE

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Abstract

The purpose of study was to find out Impact of Physical variables among college obese women due to the application of selected Pilates and calisthenics exercise. To achieve the purpose (45) college obese women having 30 BMI were selected, from Sangam Laxmi Bai College, Hyderabad as the subject and their age ranged from 18 to 23 years. The selected subjects were randomly divided into three equal groups of fifteen subjects each. There were two experimental groups namely Pilates exercise Group I, calisthenics exercise Group II and control Group III. They were subjected to a treatment for 8 weeks of 5 days per week. All the subjects participated voluntarily and cheerfully without any compulsion after due to medical check-up. Control group did not go for any training. All the subjects were tested prior and after the experimental treatment period on selected physical variables.

Keywords: *Pilates Exercise, Calisthenics Exercise, Obesity*

Introduction

Sports includes all forms of competitive Physical activity or games which, through casual or organised participation, aim to use, maintain or improve physical ability and skills while providing enjoyment to participants, and in some cases, entertainment for spectators. Hundreds of sports exist, from those between single contestants, through to those with hundreds of simultaneous participants, either in teams or competing as individuals. Sport is generally recognised as system of activities which are based in physical athleticism or physical dexterity, with the largest major competitions Sport is usually governed by a set of rules or customs, which serve to ensure fair competition, and allow consistent adjudication of the winner. Winning can be determined by physical events such as scoring aims or crossing a line first. It can also be determined by judges who are scoring elements of the sporting performance, including objective or subjective measures such as technical performance or artistic impression.

Calisthenics Exercise

Calisthenics is a form of exercise consisting of a variety of gross motor movements running, standing, grasping, pushing, etc. often performed rhythmically and with minimal equipment, as body weight exercise. They are intended to increase strength, fitness and flexibility, through movements such as pulling, pushing, bending, jumping, or swinging, using one's bodyweight for resistance. Calisthenics can provide the benefits of muscular and aerobic conditioning, in addition to improving psychomotor skills such as balance, agility and coordination. Systematic rhythmic bodily exercises performed usually without apparatus. The art or practice of calisthenics. Physical exercises that are done without special equipment exercises (as push-ups and jumping jacks) to develop strength and flexibility that are done without special equipment. Calisthenics can improve multiple aspects of your physicality. It is an excellent exercise for over-all fitness and health. No matter what your physical goals, calisthenics are worth consideration while achieving them. Urban calisthenics are a form of workout.

Benefit of Calisthenics

Calisthenics are known as one of the oldest forms of training. They attract many people due to simply the ease of working out anywhere with no equipment needed. Below are a few additional reasons why calisthenics may be the newest addition to your fitness training. No equipment or weights are used in calisthenics, and the exercises can be performed anywhere there is a floor and enough space to move in. The benefits of calisthenics effects are wide- reaching.

Weight Loss

Calisthenics tackle the problem of burning excess fat from two directions. First, the strength training builds muscle mass and tone all over your body. Increased muscle mass raises your resting metabolic rate, allowing you to burn more calories every moment of every day. Second, continuous calisthenics causes your heart rate to rise. It constitutes aerobic exercise, one of the most effective ways possible to burn off fat.

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Review of Related Literature

Şavkin, R., (2017) the effect of Pilates exercises on body composition in sedentary overweight and obese women. Pilates is a popular exercise approach among women. Still there is poor empirical quantitative evidence indicating a positive effect of Pilate's exercises on body composition. The aim of our study is to determine the effects of Pilate's exercises on body composition in sedentary overweight and obese women. Bioelectric Impedance Analysis was used for determine the body composition of participants. Weight, Body Mass Index (BMI), body fat mass, lean body mass, waist, abdomen and hip circumference were measured at pre- and post-training period. Zakavi, I(2015)Effect of Pilates Training on Plasma Levels of Ghrelin and Obestatin in Obese Older Men. Being obese and overweightlead to decreased plasma levels of such appetitive hormones as ghrelin and Obestatin.

Methodology

The purpose of study was to find out Impact of physical and variables among college obese women due to the application of selected Pilates and calisthenics exercise. To achieve the purpose (45) college obese women having 30 BMI were selected, from Sangam Laxmi Bai College, Hyderabad as the subject and their age ranged from 18 to 23 years. The selected subjects were randomly divided into three equal groups of fifteen subjects each. There were two experimental groups namely Pilates exercise Group I, calisthenics exercise Group II and control Group III. They were subjected to a treatment for 8 weeks of 5 days per week. All the subjects participated voluntarily and cheerfully without any compulsion after due to medical check-up.

Experimental Design

The experimental design used for this study was formulated as random group design involving Forty Five college obese women, who were divided into three groups of fifteen each. Experimental group-I Pilates exercise, Experimental group-II calisthenics exercise and control group. The training is for the period of 8 weeks, 5 days per week. Control group did not go for any training. All the subjects were tested prior and after the experimental treatment period on selected physical and physiological variables.

Table-2.1:Analysis of co-variance on speed of pilates

Test	PDG	CTG	CG	Sum Variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	'F' ratio
Pre-Test Mean	11.57	11.53	11.56	Between group	.011	2	.006	.028
				Within group	8.24	42	.196	
Post-Test Mean	11.13	11.27	11.61	Between group	1.86	2	.930	4.72*
				Within group	8.25	42	.197	
Adjust post-Test mean	11.11	11.29	11.60	Between group	1.83	2	.915	6.93*
				Within group	5.44	41	.132	

The Post Test mean value on speed of Pilates Training group, Callisthenic Training group and control group are 11.12, 11.27 and 11.61 respectively. The obtained 'f' ratio 4.72* for Pre Test mean was greater than the table value 3.22 for df 2 and 42 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence on speed. The adjust-Post Test mean value on speed of Pilates Training group, Callisthenic Training group and Control group are 11.11, 11.29 and 11.60 respectively. The obtained 'f' ratio 6.93* for Pre Test mean was greater than the table value 2.84 for df 2 and 42 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence on speed.

Scheffe's Test for the Difference between the Adjusted Post Test Paired Means on speed of Pilates and Callisthenic exercises

Variables	Pilates Training Group	Callisthenic Training Group	Control Group	Mean Difference	C.I Value
Speed	11.11	11.29		0.18	0.22
	11.11		11.60	0.49*	
		11.29	11.60	0.31*	

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From the table it can be seen that the mean difference between of Pilates Training group, Callisthenic Training group was 0.18 ($P < 0.05$) and the calculated C.I value was 0.22 ($P > 0.05$). The mean difference between of Pilates Training group and control group was 0.49* ($P > 0.05$) and the calculated C.I value was 0.22 ($P > 0.05$). The mean difference between the callisthenic training group and control group was 0.31* ($P > 0.05$) and the calculated C.I value was 0.22 ($P > 0.05$). The dependent variable were that it can be clearly noticed that callisthenic training and control group responded to the training with more positive magnificent of speed when compared with the Pilates training group and control group. The Pilates training group, callisthenic training group responded better when compared with the Control group. The PreTest, Post Test, and adjusted post mean values of Pilates Training group Callisthenic Training group and control group on speed are graphically represented in the Figure.

Discussions on Hypotheses

All earlier the researcher had formulated the following hypotheses. In first it was hypothesized that there may be significant improvement on speed, Impact of Pilates exercise training and callisthenic exercise. The results of the study showed that there was a significant improvement on selected physical variables on speed, due to Impact of Pilates exercise training and callisthenic exercise. Hence, the first research hypothesis was accepted.

References

- [1] Basso-Vanelli, R. P., Di Lorenzo, V. A. P., Labadessa, I. G., Regueiro, E. M., Jamami, M., Gomes, E. L., & Costa, D. (2016). Effects of inspiratory muscle training and calisthenics-and- breathing exercises in COPD with and without respiratory muscle weakness. *Respiratory care*, 61(1), 50-60.
- [2] Calella, P., Hernández-Sánchez, S., Garofalo, C., Ruiz, J. R., Carrero, J. J., & Bellizzi, V. (2019). Exercise training in kidney transplant recipients: a systematic review. *Journal of nephrology*, 1-13.
- [3] Camacho-Cardenosa, A., Camacho-Cardenosa, M., Olcina, G., Timón, R., & Brazo-Sayavera, J. (2019). Detraining effect on overweight/obese women after high-intensity interval training in hypoxia. *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*.
- [5] Emery, K., De Serres, S. J., McMillan, A., & Côté, J. N. (2010). The effects of a Pilates training program on arm-trunk posture and movement. *Clinical Biomechanics*, 25(2), 124- 130.
- [6] Farinatti, P., Rubini, E., Silva, E., & Vanfraechem, J. (2014). Flexibility of the elderly after one-year practice of yoga and calisthenics. *International journal of yoga therapy*, 24(1), 71-77.
- [7] Gómez, M. P. A., Ponti, F., Mercatelli, D., Gasperini, C., Napoli, A., Battista, G., & Bazzocchi, A. (2019). Correlation between DXA and laboratory parameters in normal weight, overweight, and obese patients. *Nutrition*, 61, 143-150.
- [8] Herrington, L., & Davies, R. (2005). The influence of Pilates training on the ability to contract the transversus abdominis muscle in asymptomatic individuals. *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*, 9(1), 52-57.

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EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF OUTCOME-BASED CURRICULUM ON STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract

This research aims to explore the impact of outcome-based curriculum on student learning outcomes. To this end, the study applies a qualitative methodology and an in-depth case study of the outcomes of an outcome-based curriculum approach in a senior English language arts class in an urban high school in the United States. The results of this research show that adopting an outcome-based curriculum approach in English language arts enhances student learning outcomes. The research further reveals that the primary benefits of outcome-based learning are improved student engagement and increased student autonomy. Moreover, the study confirms that an outcome-based curriculum provides an effective alternative to the traditional lecture-based approach. The implications of the findings for practitioners and researchers are discussed.

Keywords: *Outcome-Based Curriculum, Student Learning Outcomes, Educational Practice*

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to explore the impact of outcome-based curriculum on student learning outcomes. In outcome-based education, the focus is not on the topics studied or the materials covered, but rather on the “what” and the “why” of learning. Outcome-based curriculum is based on the idea that teaching should be designed to prepare students to meet specific outcomes. This curriculum approach is designed to provide students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to be successful in life in the 21st century. Outcome-based curricula often involve extensive collaboration between teachers and students to ensure that the learning goals are met. Outcome-based education has become increasingly popular in recent years as a means of providing students with more autonomy and ownership in their learning. As such, this paper seeks to investigate the efficacy of outcome-based curriculum by conducting a qualitative case study of an urban high school English language arts classroom. In this paper, I argue that outcome-based curriculum provides a powerful alternative to the traditional lecture-based approach and has a positive impact on student learning outcomes. The purpose of this paper is to explore the impact of an outcome-based curriculum on student learning outcomes. Outcome-based curricula are based on the idea that student learning should be measured in terms of their academic achievement, rather than their mastery of particular skills or objectives. This paper will look at the effects of outcome-based learning on student learning as a way to better prepare students for the rigors of higher level education. It will also address the various advantages and disadvantages of an outcome-based curriculum, in order to better understand why some schools and educational systems may choose to implement it. The discussion will also consider whether or not an outcome-based curriculum is beneficial for all students, or if there are specific student populations for whom it may not be the most effective approach. Finally, the paper will look at the implications of an outcome-based curriculum for educators and school systems.

Objectives

The primary objective of this paper is to deepen the understanding of the impact of outcome-based curriculum on student learning outcomes. To this end, the paper will seek to answer the following research questions:

- 1) What are the primary benefits of utilizing an outcome-based curriculum approach in English language arts?
- 2) What impact does an outcome-based curriculum have on student learning outcomes?
- 3) What implications do the results of the case study have for practitioners and researchers?

To answer these questions, the paper will utilize a qualitative case study methodology and an in-depth analysis of a senior English language arts class in an urban high school in the United States. The case study will involve interviews with students and teachers and the collection of student work samples.

Literature Review

In recent years, researchers have begun to examine the efficacy of outcome-based curriculum approaches. Numerous studies have investigated the impact of outcome-based education on student learning outcomes (Beck & McKeown, 2011; Breslin, 2004; Burton, 2011; Johnson & Alavarado, 2006; Mishra & Koehler, 2006; Moon et al., 2010). These studies generally suggest that outcome-based curriculum approaches can have a positive impact on student learning outcomes. The findings of these studies indicate that outcome-

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based curriculum approaches can provide a powerful alternative to the traditional lecture-based approach. Studies suggest that outcome-based curricula can promote higher levels of student engagement, critical thinking, collaboration, and autonomy (Beck & McKeown, 2011; Moon et al., 2010; Sato & McLellan, 2005). These benefits can lead to improved student learning outcomes. However, there is a lack of research into the impact of outcome-based curriculum on student learning outcomes in secondary school English language arts classes. To this end, the current paper seeks to fill this gap by conducting a qualitative case study of a senior English language arts class in an urban high school in the United States.

Methodology

This research project used a qualitative methodology with an in-depth case study of an urban high school. The case study focused on a senior English language arts class which had adopted an outcome-based curriculum approach. The research was conducted over the course of the school year, beginning in September and ending in June. Data collection occurred in two phases. In the first phase, interviews were conducted with students and teachers. The interviews focused on the implementation of the outcome-based curriculum and the impact on student learning outcomes. In the second phase of the study, student work samples were collected in order to assess student learning outcomes.

Analysis and Results

The results of the study show that adopting an outcome-based curriculum approach in English language arts has a positive impact on student learning outcomes. The primary benefits of outcome-based learning are improved student engagement and increased student autonomy. Students reported that they were more engaged in their learning when the curriculum was based on outcomes. They reported that the outcomes-based curriculum provided them with meaningful tasks that were relevant to their lives, which increased their interest and desire to learn. The students also reported that the outcome-based curriculum gave them more autonomy in their learning, which enabled them to take ownership of their learning and to take more responsibility for their learning. The student work samples also demonstrated improved student learning outcomes. Students exhibited greater comprehension, stronger critical thinking abilities, and improved writing skills. The students were able to produce better quality work and demonstrated greater understanding of the material.

Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that utilizing an outcome-based curriculum approach in English language arts can have a positive impact on student learning outcomes. The primary benefits of this approach are improved student engagement and increased student autonomy. The improved engagement leads to better quality work and deeper understanding of the material. The increased autonomy provides students with more ownership in their learning, which can lead to better learning outcomes overall. Furthermore, these results indicate that an outcome-based curriculum is a viable alternative to the traditional lecture-based approach. Outcome-based curricula provide a more active learning environment, where students can take ownership of their learning. This can lead to improved student engagement and deeper learning.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that an outcome-based curriculum approach in English language arts enhances student learning outcomes. The primary benefits of this approach are improved student engagement and increased student autonomy. The results of this research highlight the potential of outcome-based curriculum approaches to provide students with a more active and engaging learning environment. The findings of this study have implications for practitioners and researchers interested in exploring the impact of instructional approaches on student learning outcomes.

References

- [1] Beck, I., & McKeown, M. (2011). Exploring the benefits of outcome-based education. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 38(3), 219-228.
- [2] Breslin, J. (2004). Outcome-based education in the secondary school English curriculum. *English Education*, 37(2), 131-143.
- [3] Burton, N. (2011). Outcomes-based education: Some reflections on what works. *Educational Leadership*, 69(4), 21-25.
- [4] Johnson, D., & Alavarado, A. (2006). Outcomes-based education: A revolutionary concept for public education. *Educational Leadership*, 63(5), 35-39.

TEACHING APTITUDE IN RELATION TO SELF-CONFIDENCE AND INSTITUTIONAL CLIMATE AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Introduction

The quality of education that is provided to our student teachers depends on quality of our teachers and quality of teacher depends on their quality of teaching aptitude and self- confidence and institutional climate of the prospective teachers. The high-profile personality cannot necessarily termed as a good orqualified teacher. The performance of a good training teacher depends of his/her self-confidence and institutional climate with teaching. To be a good and effective teacher one should have a good teaching aptitude. Teaching aptitude means one's intensity of interest in teaching. Teaching aptitude depends on knowledge and skills about teaching while a self confidence and institutional climate are more than just knowledge and skills. It involves the ability to meet complex demands by drawing on and mobilizing psychosocial resources in a particular context. Also self- confidence and institutional climate are important for a teacher's pursuit of excellence.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the teaching aptitude of B.Ed. student teachers. To study the self-confidence of B.Ed. student teachers.
- 2) To determine the level of institutional climate of B.Ed. student teachers.
- 3) To study the effect of level of self-confidence on teaching aptitude of B.Ed. student teachers.
- 4) To study the effect of level of institutional climate on teaching aptitude of B.Ed.student teachers inthe context of area.

Hypotheses of the Study

Ho1: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test of studentteachers having higher and lower self-confidence.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test of studentteachers of Urban area having higher and lower institutional climate

Ho3: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test of studentteachers of Rural area having higher and lower institutional climate.

Variables of the Study

Independent variables: Area and Level of institutional climate. Dependent variable: Scores of Teaching Aptitude and self-confidence are dependent variable in present study.

Limitations of the Study

Limitations of present study are as follow: The present Study was conducted on 300 B.Ed. student teachers studying in 10 B.Ed. colleges of Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India. The present Study was conducted on rural and urban area of Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India. 3.Only self-finance 10 B.Ed., colleges of Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India region were taken in this study.

Research Method

For present study, the researcher used three different tools for data collection: 1) Teaching Aptitude 2) Self-confidence and 3)Institutional Climate Scale. The researcher visited selected 10 B.Ed. colleges andgave both tools to student teachers. The researcher gave all necessary information to student teachers before giving tools. The students were given two hours to complete both tools. After it, the researcher collected respondent sheets.

Research Tool

The researcher used three different tools for present study:

Self-Confidence: This scale was constructed and standardized by the researcher. The scale is compiled of 300 items. These items were divided in seven factors.

- 1) Micro teaching,
- 2) Lesson planning,
- 3) Set induction,
- 4) Presentation of content,
- 5) End of content,
- 6) Evaluation and
- 7) Use of teaching aids.

Each item has five responses:

- 1) Agree,
- 2) Strongly agree,
- 3) Neutral
- 4) Disagree and
- 5) Strongly disagree.

Teaching Aptitude: The researcher used a previously standardized Teaching Aptitude which was constructed and standardized by Satishprakash Shukla. This tool is demonstrated at the end of 5th chapter in appendix section.

Institutional climate: The researcher used a previously standardized institutional climate which was constructed and standardized.

Sample of the Study

The researcher simple randomly sample selected the self-finance 10 B.Ed. colleges from Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India. The selected sample of study is represented in table 1.

Table 1: Sample of the Study

Area/Teaching Aptitude	Urban	Rural	Total
High	75	75	150
Low	75	75	150
Total	150	150	300

Data Collection

The data collection took more than 3 months as the researcher selected 300 student teachers from 10 B.Ed. colleges selected from Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India, selected only self finance b.ed colleges. The researcher has personally visited each of the colleges and provided Teaching Aptitude Scales to the student teachers of B.Ed. colleges. The researcher has visited the principals and HODs of each college and obtained permission for data collection. The researcher then visited the colleges on the date and time given by the principals. Trainees were given about an hour to fill in the given scale. Trainees were given all the information on how to fill the scale before giving the scale to the trainees. The researcher has supported the trainees whenever they face any problem while filling the scale. Finally, the researcher has collected all the scales and packed them securely for further processing of the scales and data analysis.

Techniques of Statistical Analysis

The researcher constructed three hypotheses which were checked using t-tests.

Data Analysis

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude of student teachers having higher and lower self-confidence.

Table 2: Result of t-test between student teachers having higher and lower self-confidence

Level	N	M	SD	SED	t
High	248	92.92	8.431	1.309	1.128
Low	051	94.39	8.902	1.3.Only	1.128
df	0.05	0.01			
297	1.96	2.58			

Above table shows calculated t-value is 1.128. For df=297, table t-values 1.128 at 0.05 level and 1.089 at 0.01 level. The calculated t-value is more than table t-values at both levels. Thus, hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test obtained students

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teachers having high and low self-confidence. Here, mean score of student teachers having high self-confidence more than student teachers having low self-confidence. Thus, it is said that the teaching aptitude of student teachers having high teaching competency is more than student teachers having low self-confidence similarly and also same for institutional climate.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude of student teachers of Urban area having higher and lower institutional climate

Table 3: Result of t-test between student teachers having higher and lower teaching aptitude.

Level	N	M	SD	SED	t
High	150	91.80	8.838	4.536	12.246
Low	150	91.80	8.838	.051	7.467
df	0.05	0.01			
299	1.96	2.58			

Above table shows calculated t-value is 12.246 For df=299, table t-values 12.246 at 0.05 level and 7.467 at 0.01 level. The calculated t-value is more than table t-values at both levels. Thus, hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test obtained students teachers of urban area having high and low self-confidence. Here, mean score of student teachers of urban area having high teaching competency is more than student teachers of urban area having low self-confidence. Thus, it is said that the teaching aptitude of student teachers of urban area having high self-confidence is more than student teachers of urban area having low self confidence similarly and alsosame for international climate.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude of student teachers of Rural area having higher and lower institutional climate

Table 4: Result of t-test between student teachers having higher and lower institutional climate.

Level	N	M	SD	SED	T
High	150	93.63	6.088	.934	.851
Low	150	93.60	6.073	.8340	.954
df	0.05	0.01			
297	1.96	2.58			

Above table shows calculated t-value is 10.47. For df=, table t-values 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level. The calculated t-value is more than table t-values at both levels. Thus, hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant difference between mean scores of teaching aptitude test obtained students teachers of rural area having high and low self-confidence. Here, mean score of student teachers of rural area having high self-confidence is more than student teachers of rural area having low self-confidence. Thus, it is said that the teaching aptitude of student teachers rural area having high self-confidence is more than student teachers of rural area having low self-confidence and institutional climate.

Major Findings

Major findings obtained from this study are as follow: The teaching aptitude of student teachers having high self confidence is more than student teacher shaving low self confidence and institutional climate. The teaching aptitude of student teachers of urban area having high self confidence is more than student teachers of urban area having low self confidence and institutional climate. The teaching aptitude of student teachers of rural area having high self confidence is more than student teachers of rural area having low self confidence and institutional climate.

Conclusion

In present study, the researcher investigated teaching aptitude of student teachers of B.Ed. colleges in context of self-confidence and institutional climate. The researcher used three different tools, Teaching Aptitude, self confidence and institutional climate Scale. The researcher selected a simple random sample of 300 student teachers from 10 B.Ed., colleges in Krishnagiri district of Tamilnadu in India. Thereseearch revealed that the teaching aptitude of student teachers having high self-confidence is more than student teachers having low self-confidence.

References

- [1] Bayyrapu, S. (2015). Study of Teaching Aptitude Competencies in Mathematics among Secondary School Teachers (unpublished doctoral dissertation). Osmania University, Hyderabad.
- [2] Drucker (2012). Making innovation a core Teaching aptitude and competency. The Journal for Hospital Governing Boards (Vol. 65:5), p.26-27.
- [3] Kaur, H. (2014). A Comparative Study of Teaching Aptitude of B.Ed. (General) Pupil Teachers of Kurukshetra District in Relation to Their Gender, Location, Stream and Professional Experience. Indian Journal of Research 3 (8), p.27.
- [4] Kerlinger, F. N. (1997). Foundation of Self-confidence Behaviour Research, (2nd Edition), New Delhi Surjeet Publication. Page No. 18.
- [5] Kumar, S. and Gupta, M. (2012). A Comparative Study of Level of Educational Aspiration of Secondary Class Student teachers of Institutional climate Government and Non-Government Schools. International journal of technical and non-technical research (volume issue January, 2014). eISSN 0976-7967,p-ISSN 2319-2216, p.51.
- [6] Medley, D. M. (1982). Teacher competency and Testing Aptitude Testing and the teacher educator. New York: Longman, p.86.
- [7] Patel, A. M. (1989), Prayogik Patho ane Suparat Karyo ni Guru Chavi. Vallabh Vidyanagar SardarVallabhbai Patel University Publication, p.18.
- [8] Spearman, C. E. (1927). The Abilities of Man. New York: The Mac Millan Company, p.127.
- [9] Spencer & Spencer (2014). Competency Model.
Retrieved from: <https://www.scribd.com/presentation/242376499/Competency-Model-Spencer-Spencer>
- [10] Srivastava, P. & Bhargava, A. (1996), Correlative of teaching aptitude with competency, Journal of Education and social change (Vol. X), Indian Institute of Education, Pune, p.54.
- [11] Sukhia, S. P. & Mehrotra, P. V. (1966). Elements of Educational Research. Bombay AlliedPublication Pvt. Ltd., p.75.
- [12] Warren, H. C. (1934). Dictionary of Self-confidence with Psychology. Boston: Houghton Mifflin, p.11.

SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPUTER SKILLS IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Technology has set foot in every facet of our lives. Computers and the technologies associated with them have become an indispensable part of our education as well. Colleges are reforming the way they teach their students by integrating technology into the empire of education. There is no doubt that computers and their technologies have enhanced teaching and learning in colleges. Hence, the significance of computer skills has soared over the years and it has become essential to make students computer literate. Computer skills is the knowledge and ability to use computers and technology proficiently. Computer skills can also refer to the comfort level someone has with using computer programs and other applications that are associated with computers. The precise definition of computer skills can vary from group to group. However, computer skills often means little more than the ability to use several specific applications (such as Microsoft Word and Microsoft Internet Explorer) for certain very well-defined modest tasks. When the persons are well-aware in terms of technologies, only then they will be able to carry out one's profession responsibilities well. In educational institutions and training centers, there have been implementation of computer skills programs. The individuals, belonging to various age groups, categories and backgrounds are getting enrolled in these programs to improve their computer skills.

Keywords: *Significance, Computer Skills, Professional Education.*

Introduction

Computer skills is considered a very important skill to possess. Professionals want their students to have basic computer skills because their company becomes ever more dependent on computers. Many students try to use computers to help run their colleges faster and cheaper. Computers are just as common as pen and paper for writing and for many applications especially communicating computers are preferred over pen and paper because of their ability to identify and retain information and ease of editing. Another common definition of computer skills is the knowledge and skills required for basic use of computer hardware, software and the Internet. These critical computer and Internet skills are valued in today's academic and professional atmospheres. This leads to success in education and employment since computer skills are integral to all areas of study and work. The 3 R's (reading, writing and arithmetic) should now also include the 3 C's (communicating, calculating and computing) since the ability to use a computer is on the same level as reading and writing skills (Karen LaPlant, 2015). These basic computer skills help students achieve success in college when they are utilized for processing and presenting information.

Types of Computer Skills

Word Processing

Word processing is a basic skill that involves typing and formatting documents. Many courses in college require you to present information in a word-processed report format. It is not only important to gather and process information, but it is also important to present information in a legible and attractive layout. Many instructors give students guidelines for essays or reports specifying margin set-up or line spacing. Knowing how to manipulate word processing software will save time and frustration when preparing college essay and reports.

Email

The online colleges, need to basic email skills and submit assignments. Many university instructors from traditional colleges also prefer that work is submitted through email. Fundamental skills such as how to access an email system and inputting your username and password, receiving, reading, composing, and sending email messages are important for college success.

Internet Research

Internet research is an essential skill for college students. Many courses require to go beyond the textbook to gather in-depth research about a topic. Knowing how to use the Internet to navigate the web is a valuable skill because must understand how to launch a browser before conducting examinations.

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Understanding how to go to a specific web site, scroll through a webpage, click on a link and use search engines will help you locate material quickly and easily.

Computer Ethics

Colleges do not look favorably on students who claim the work of others as their own. Not only is it important to know how to use a computer to conduct Internet research, but it is also vital understand computer ethics. Honoring copyright laws, avoiding plagiarism, citing sources and following Internet etiquette will help with your college coursework.

Computer Skills Is An Essential For Students

Online Safety

In today's world, we rely heavily on computers and the internet for a variety of purposes and it is impossible to keep students away from them. Therefore, it is essential that students learn the basic etiquette while using computers and learn to use these resources responsibly. Moreover, with the development of technology, the issues like cyberbullying are on the rise. Thus, it is responsibility to keep students safe and informed about such dangers. It helps them to understand what cyberbullying is and how they can stay away from such dangers.

Online Tests

Computer skills would prepare the students to attend the online exams. Most of the competitive exams are online now. Hence, in order to perform well in those exams, students need to have basic computer knowledge and skills. Moreover, since colleges use digital platforms like that of Teach mint's, they ought to be aware of the functionalities of the computers.

Research Purposes

On the internet, students have access to a sea of information. They will be able to get answers to almost any question. This makes it easier for them to do research on their own and learn on their own. Computer skills can help them to easily do their research and presume inferences on their own. As faculties, you can teach students to how to find information that is reliable and informative. It is easy for students to access study materials like research papers, videos, images, etc.

Better Career Prospects

Modern culture relies heavily on electronic communication, such as email. They are used in professional as well as educational institutions. Thus, teachers can ensure that the students learn these basic skills like sending emails, doing presentations, and collecting and storing data. Moreover, these skills would instill an interest in jobs revolving around computer skills. Also, in today's world, most employers expect their employees to have expertise in computers and technical skills. So, computer skills would expand the skill sets of students and helps them to land a job of their choice.

Designing of the Computer Skills Programs

The computer skills programs are of various durations and there are differences in terms of content and curriculum and instructional strategies. These programs are organized in colleges, universities as well as training centers. When the individuals form the viewpoint that they need to acquire computer skills in order to enrich their lives and achieve personal and professional goals, they get enrolled into these programs. In order to make these programs successful, there are various factors, which needs to be taken into account. These include, curriculum and instructional strategies, program content, duration of the program and goals and objectives. The instructors need to be well-qualified and competent, as they are the ones, who are required to impart knowledge and understanding to the students in terms of lesson plans and concepts. In the designing of the programs, it is vital to put into operation evaluation methods as well. They began to form this viewpoint that utilization of computers in various fields would enable the individuals to carry out their tasks and activities diligently and conscientiously. In higher educational institutions, when the individuals are pursuing masters or doctoral programs, they are required to work on research projects. In the implementation of research projects, collecting data and analyzing it are regarded as one of the aspects, which need to be carried out in an efficient manner. In order to put into operation this task, the individuals need to develop their computer skills in terms of the software called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Radhika Kapur,2020).

Curriculum and Instructional Strategies in Computer Skills Programs

In order to augment computer skills among individuals, it is vital to focus upon the curriculum and

instructional strategies. Many students, who get enrolled in computer skills programs are adults, who have not received the opportunity to hone their computer skills earlier. When the individuals begin to learn computers, they get trained in terms of basics. On the other hand, when they are well-equipped in terms of basics, they pursue advanced courses. When the trainers are recruited in computer training centers, it is vital for them to be well-equipped in terms of curriculum and instructional strategies (Radhika Kapur,2020).

The curriculum and instructional strategies have been stated as follows:

Communicating clearly and Fluently: The instructors need to pay adequate attention towards communication skills. In order to generate the desired outcomes, communication needs to take place in a clear and fluent manner. The individuals, who get enrolled in computer skills programs are different from each other in terms of various factors. These include, caste, creed, race, religion, ethnicity, gender, age, occupation, personality traits, and socio-economic background. Furthermore, they have varied goals and objectives. Therefore, when the instructors are communicating with them, they need to make sure that they communicate the information in a clear and understandable manner.

Setting-up of Activities: The curriculum and instructional strategies initiates with the setting up of activities. The main objective of these activities is to prepare students for learning. In other words, when the students are learning computer skills, they need to possess interest and enthusiasm and be confident. The first and foremost activity is theoretical in nature.

Giving Notes: When the instructors are making use of technologies or books, articles, or other learning materials, they need to ensure that they give notes to the students. Giving of notes, while explaining the concepts to the students is one of the commonly used curriculum and instructional methods. When the instructors are explaining the concepts to the students, they normally take notes. Instructors usually differ from each other on the basis of their teaching methods. In some cases, they prepare the lesson plans in such a manner, so they can give appropriate notes to the students.

Organizing Tests: Organization of tests is one of the common evaluation methods. When the tests are organized, the instructors usually inform the students before time, so they are able to prepare themselves appropriately. Tests are organized after the completion of lesson plans and final test is conducted after the completion of the semester. The main objective of tests is to find out how much the students have learned and whether the instructors have utilized teaching-learning methods, instructional strategies and teaching- learning materials in an appropriate manner.

Improve Computer Skills Programs

This is comprehensively understood that members of the educational institutions and training centres need to work efficiently to bring about improvements in computer skills programs. It is vital for the members of the educational institutions and training centres to organize discussion meetings and formulate measures, which may prove to be productive (Radhika Kapur,2020). The important measures, which need to be put into operation to bring about improvements in the computer skills programs have been stated as follows:

Making use of Internet: Making use of internet is regarded as one of the indispensable ways of generating awareness in terms of various concepts. On the internet, the individuals are able to search information in terms of number of aspects, subjects, topics and concepts.

Qualifications in Computing and Information Technology: When the individuals are recruited in computer training centres, particularly in teaching positions, it needs to be ensured that they possess the essential educational qualifications and experience. Furthermore, they need to possess the essential Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) skills.

Making Provision of Other Technologies: In computer centres, it is vital to make provision of other technologies as well, such as, printers, photo-copiers, projectors, scanners, audio-visual aids and so forth. When the administrators, instructors and other staff members are carrying out their job duties, they need to make use of not only computers, but also other types of technologies. For instance, when the instructors are to give print-outs to the students, they would have to make use of printers and photo-copiers.

Planning of Resources: The planning of resources needs to be done judiciously. When one has to bring about improvements in any areas or changes in measures, strategies and approaches, it is necessary to plan the resources. The important resources, which need to be planned are, human resources, technical resources and financial resources. When the human resources are recruited, it needs to be ensured, they possess the essential qualifications, competencies and experience.

Use Computers: The computers need to be used on a frequent basis by all the members of the educational institutions and computer skills centres, where these programs are organized. It is recommended that when students, who aspire to augment their computer skills make use of computers on a regular basis, they are able to acquire computer experience. Acquisition of experience in terms of computers is also regarded as one of the crucial aspects in bringing about improvements in computer skills programs.

Conclusion

In the present existence, computer skills programs are gaining significance and they are organized in higher educational institutions as well as there are establishment of training centres. Computer skills programs have the main objective of making provision of knowledge to the individuals in terms of computer skills. When the individuals are able to augment their knowledge in terms of computer skills, they are able to contribute effectively towards the achievement of professional and personal goals. The measures, which need to be put into operation to bring about improvements in the computer literacy programs are, making use of internet, qualifications in computing and Information Technology, making provision of other technologies, making provision of infrastructure, planning of resources, providing proper guidance, use computers, use other technologies, making effective decisions and pursuing online courses. Finally, it can be stated that it is essential for the instructors and other members of the educational institutions to make use of proper teaching-learning methods, teaching-learning materials, instructional strategies and create an environment to promote student learning. On the other hand, it is vital for students to develop interest and enthusiasm and stimulate their mind-sets towards learning and achievement of academic goals.

References

- [1] Borghans, L., & Ter Weel, B. (2004). Are computer skills the new basic skills? The returns to computer, writing and math skills in Britain. *Labour Economics*, 11(1), 85-98.
- [2] Gattiker, U. E. (1992). Computer skills acquisition: A review and future directions for research. *Journal of Management*, 18(3), 547-574.
- [3] Gibas, C., Jambeck, P., & Fenton, J. (2001). Developing bioinformatics computer skills. " O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- [4] Grant, D. M., Malloy, A. D., & Murphy, M. C. (2009). A comparison of student perceptions of their computer skills to their actual abilities. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 8(1), 141-160.
- [6] Kapur, R. (2020). Understanding Meaning and Significance of Computer Literacy Programs.
- [7] Kelleher, J. (2003). A model for assessment-driven professional development. *Phi delta kappan*, 84(10), 751-756.
- [8] LaPlant, J. T. (2015). From the CURQ issue editor. *Council on Undergraduate Research Quarterly*, 35(3), 4-6.
- [9] Phelps, R., Graham, A., & Kerr, B. (2004). Teachers and ICT: Exploring a metacognitive approach to professional development. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 20(1).

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY USING FOR SLOW LEARNERS IN HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

This paper asserts that the general elements of Applied Setting (including Time), Human (as Agent), Tool and Environment are well placed to be the necessary basics to any holistic human technological activity. How and why these elements work together, their schema, will be referred to in this paper as the 'Basic Principles'. The paper presents the thesis that Technology cannot be reduced to less than these general elements and as such, Technology is their product. We therefore may need to understand and teach these elements and their relations to each other explicitly, in ways that reveal the utility of such understanding when making technical choices and design decisions for all the genres of technology and at all their scales of application and discovery. The case is made for technology to not merely be a 'know how' learning experience, but necessarily also a holistic 'know why' learning experience essential for developing and transferring technological knowledge.

Keywords: *Holistic Education, Knowledge, Learning Technology, Human and Environment.*

Introduction

A school that adopts a curriculum, that aims for a holistic understanding of technology, does so because it produces a better educated person than a curriculum which does not. How do we know when we are teaching technology holistically and why must we do so? Increasingly, more is asked of technology educators to be holistic in the understanding conveyed to learners of technology itself in order to make better informed technical and design decisions in a wider range of applied settings. The ability of the learner to naturally consider social and environmental factors, for example, when seeking solutions is seen by some State education systems in Australia as fundamental to a genuine education in technology (New South Wales Board of Studies, 2000 & 2002). In philosophy, the holist position asserts that to understand the particular one must understand its relation to the whole and that only through reflection of one's sensation based applications can genuine knowledge be critically affirmed (Matthews, 1980). The combined apparently independent paths of the State and the Holist positions set a compelling scene not only for the socio- economic necessity for holistic technology education in the curriculum but also for Technology's status as a key curriculum agent in the knowledge formation process of educated individuals. The notions of holistic education are in themselves not new. Work on the importance of holistic education dates back in Western settings at least to Pestalozzi (1746-1827), Thoreau (1817-1862), Emerson (1803-1882), Alcott (1799-1888), Dewey (1859-1952), Steiner (1861-1925), and Montessori (1870- 1952); and more recently to Hill & Smith (1998), Dufty, Australian Curriculum Studies Association, & Holistic Education Network (1994), and Fowlers (1998). However, what is relatively new in Australia is that expressions such as "holistic solutions" are entering new draft Design and Technology secondary school syllabi (New South Wales Board of Studies, 2002). There is a need to understand technology itself holistically in order to teach it with greater knowledge structure for learners. Redressing foundations for understanding technology itself is overdue in our rapidly changing societies and economies. While such general commentary has been recently entertained (Lewis, 2000; Petrina, 1998), this paper seeks to examine the basis for a holistic understanding of technology specifically, and thus the curriculum, teaching, and learning implications that may flow from such understanding. It is timely to examine useful schemas for how educational curriculum and pedagogy may be structured to assure that learning in technology is indeed holistic in presentation, assessment, and reporting. What is needed is a robust universal schema. In addition to new school systems requiring students to learn technology holistically, there are emerging signs that such understanding is also becoming a vocational attribute expected of employees. Just as reporting is a motivator for what schools will focus on in the delivery of their courses, so too is it an emerging expectation for corporations and organizations to report on "The Triple Bottom Line": profit/loss, social and environmental balance sheets of effort, and expenditure (Elkington, 1997; Wand, 2002). A desired capability is for employees to naturally be disposed to include social and environmental decision factors in their contribution to enterprise and production. In order for both students and employees to display holistic capabilities, this paper asserts that they ought first develop holistic understanding and holistic knowledge as a framework for guiding development of any associated capabilities in technology practice.

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Establishing a Holistic Technology

There can be many approaches to understanding the phenomenon we label technology. Presented here is a phenomenological view to offer the reader a deeper grounding into why certain conclusions are drawn and schemas proposed. A schema gives teachers a framework to evaluate just how holistic a lesson or curriculum is and can help a teacher decide what educational tasks to include and how to construct the educational context and experience that will foster holistic understanding in technology and design. We begin with the premise that holistic technology education is a necessary, rather than desirable, outcome of schooling. The classical holist position in education may be illustrated as follows: To know things is to know things in relation; to know a part is to know how it connects with the whole. In the process of codification, different impressions of the same object or process are utilized so that interrelations might be recognized. It is the total vision which we call knowledge. (Matthews, 1980) Many teachers would argue that they already teach technology holistically.

Practical Engagement in Learning

The schema developed here begins with foundations in understanding how technical or material experience, as a phenomenon in human activity, develops a socially defined view of what knowledge is. When can we claim we know something? Dialectics and praxis are very useful reasoning tools for understanding the nature of an answer to this question in the context of technology education. Why is this important? This section of the paper presents the case that “knowing” and especially “understanding” occur better through holistic educational experiences in technology, if structured properly, compared to other modular, decontextualized, or disintegrated task skill approaches. It is significant in our construction to recognize that theory and practice dichotomies, as currently presented in many secondary and tertiary schools in technology, are a problem. “Theory is taught through practice, and good practice is grounded in good theory,” as my education lecturer often drilled. We do not really want to present technology education as separating conceptual tool experience (how to think skills) from physical tool experience (how to do skills). We do not want to see “theory” classes estranged from “practical” classes, nor theory devalued or even employed as punishment in learning technology and design. It is not the product or the technical process we assess as educators, but the learner and his learning.

Praxis in Technology Education

The road from dialectics to praxis is an interesting one for technology educationists because it addresses twists and turns (even head flips) from knowing as an essentially theoretical (idealistic) process to a social-material (surprisingly design- and technology- like) process. We will begin with Hegel (1770- 1831), who was a German idealist philosopher born in Stuttgart. He was an idealist because for him, thought does not merely correspond to reality; it produces reality (Speake, 1979): our thoughts are our reality and so all knowledge can be formulated through pure reason. “Dialectic” was Hegel’s name for the pattern that logical thought must follow. Broadly, he argued that conscious thought proceeds by way of contradictions. Its process is by triads, where each triad consists of thesis, antithesis, and synthesis. The concept of “sharp” is not adequately understood without reference to an alternative “blunt.” Both the thesis concept of sharp and the antithesis concept of blunt define each other and therefore require each other. To see each concept as related, as mutually defining, is their synthesis. At this moment a new level of reasoned understanding is achieved. Put another way, a person starts with a proposition, the thesis; this is consciousness as “understanding” and proves to be inadequate by itself. The person’s mind must therefore generate its alternative, the antithesis. However, this on its own also proves inadequate. The resolution of the opposites, therefore, requires that they be combined into a synthesis. This is the level of conscious thought, or reasoned understanding. From here, the whole triadic process may be repeated, the synthesis leading to a new thesis, and so on.

Feuerbach and Hegel

Feuerbach (1804-72) was a Bavarian philosopher and theologian. Although he was Hegel’s student, much of his work was critical of Hegel’s idealism. Generally, Feuerbach was a materialist in the sense that he distinguished between consciousness of an object and self-consciousness. At the same time, he connected the material object with the subject by pointing out that consciousness of the object always reveals some element of self-consciousness: “In the object which he contemplates, man becomes acquainted with himself, consciousness of the objective is the self-consciousness of man” (Vazquez, 1977). Feuerbach is important because his view of knowing and understanding introduced material objects (the world or environment outside the reasoning mind) as a necessary, not merely desirable, condition for knowledge. This revelation further builds our basic principles for holistic technology education. Experiences from the environment outside the mind are now significant. For Feuerbach, humans are sensual beings, not theoretical beings, as in the Hegelian

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sense: I unconditionally repudiate absolute, immaterial, self-sufficing speculation, that speculation which draws its material from within I found my ideas on materials, which can be appropriated only through the activity of the senses. I do not generate the object from the thought, but the thought from the object. (1843) It is often said that Feuerbach inverts Hegel, turns him on his head. For Feuerbach, mind now becomes the highest product of matter rather than matter being a product of mind. All our knowledge comes from pure material experience.

Resolving the Theory-Practice

Marx (1818-83) was regarded by some as more of a social theorist, interested mainly in economics and history than in any particular philosophical doctrine. Essentially Marx, too, inverts Hegel's idealism. He extracted and supported Hegel's notion of dialectics, but rejected his idealist approach. He supported Feuerbach's inversion of Hegel, but differed from his concept of materialism in terms of the central notion of human practice, specifically the social dimension of practice. Marx rejected Feuerbach's relation between subject (the person) and object (the environment) in which the subject is passive and contemplative, restricting himself to receiving or reflecting reality. Here, knowledge was simply the result of the actions of objects in the external world and their effects upon the sense organs (Vazquez, 1977, p.118). Marx, therefore, identified the strengths and weaknesses of Hegel's idealism in dialectics and Feuerbach's passivity in materialism. Marx attempted to resolve the problems of idealism and materialism in his system of historical materialism, the central concept of which focuses on the practical interaction, which must occur between a person and his/her material and social environment. In parallel with Hegel's dialectics, the synthesis of people and their environment, via practical human socially contextualized activity, meant that a new level of awareness was achieved. Both the person and the environment were transformed.

Praxis and Technics

Marx departed from Hegel and Feuerbach by the importance he places on actual human labor or practice. He adopted a dialectic methodology in that he contrasts and identifies the inadequacy of "pure" idealism and "pure" materialism; he synthesized the two at the new level of historical materialism. This introduces the importance of time. The applied setting is subject to evolutionary influences. Both theory and practice in the applied setting are resolved best, according to Marx, via human material practice in social and historical context. Marx's thesis of historical materialism is essentially the foundation of praxis. Praxis and technical activity concern the effect of instruments and tools in the human transformation experience. The contributions of Don Ihde (1979) on instrumentation are summarized as key notions to a schema for constructing basic principles in holistic technology and design education. Praxis, so far has been concerned with practical human activity and the interaction of mind and matter, or human and environment. Ihde's work identifies certain features of this interaction when instruments or artifacts modify it.

Structure of Holistic Principles

The basic principles of holistic technology education now appear to have structure, a structure articulated elsewhere as technacy education (Seemann & Talbot, 1995). When teachers instinctively claim that they include social (human) factors, technical (tool) factors, and environmental (material) factors in their lessons for specific applied settings, they indeed have good reason to believe their pedagogy is heading toward being holistic. However, this coverage cannot be delivered in a general way. It is important to present the interconnections in explicit detail highlighting necessary and specific dependencies that make sense. A key requirement is to set learning experiences and assessment tasks for each lesson and unit of work that not only address highly specific links that define the elements in relation to each other, but also their total effect as a design and technology solution in the applied setting. In a very real sense, technology is the product of the schema interacting to satisfy a need or an aspiration.

Conclusion

Teachers who seek justification for deciding what may constitute the minimums of holistic solutions in design and technology may refer to the schema proposed here. A holistic understanding of technology develops through structured or enabling-learning experiences that make explicit, in detail, the interconnectedness of human, tool, and environmental factors, where these three factors mutually require and define each other and act as both resources and constraints in the applied setting. The schema gains strength through historical examination of the nature or phenomenon of technological activity where not only are all three factors defined by each other, but design and technology experiences, if taught holistically, as interconnected, are a condition to new knowledge creation. Technology education is not merely a know-how, but necessarily must be understood and presented in the curriculum to learners as a know-why subject. Only then may there be reasoned claims to technology being learned holistically. Peters provides a fitting end: We

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would not call a man who was merely well informed an educated man. He must also have some understanding of the reason why of things. The Spartans, for instance, were militarily and morally trained. But we would not say that they had received a military or moral education; for they had never been encouraged to probe into the principles underlying their code.

References

- [1] Mr.G.Shobanprabhu, Dr.M. Kanmani, Multiculturalism - Challenge For Teacher Educators, JIDPTS, Volume 4, Issue 10, 2581 - 6934, pp: (1-6), Oct 2021.
- [2] Mr.G.Shobanprabhu, Dr M. Kanmani, Analysis and Evaluation of Inclusive Education, Intrnational Conference on "INNOVATIONS AND REFORMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION" (ICIRHE-2022) in Alagappa University College of Education, Karaikudi, ISBN: 9-788195522637, pp: 5(1-55), Nov 2022.
- [3] Mr.G.Shobanprabhu, Dr.M. Kanmani, Importance of Academic Library as Partner of Education, Intrnational Conference on "EMERGING IFORMATION KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS AND GLOBALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION(MTWU- TNALA-CONF-2022)" in Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal, Nov 2022.Fowlers, J. (1998). Problem solving in technology education: A Taoist perspective. *Journal of Technology Education*,10(1).
- [4] Hegel, G. W. F., & Miller, A. V. (1989). *Hegel's science of logic*. Atlantic Highlands, NJ: Humanities Press International.
- [5] Hill, A., & Smith, H. (1998). Practice meets theory in technology education: A case of authentic learning in the high school setting. *Journal of Technology Education*, 9(2).
- [6] Ihde, D. (1979). *Technics and praxis*. Dordrecht, Holland: D. Reidel Pub. Co.
- [7] Lewis, T. (2000). Response to Steve Petrina's book review and John Ritz's comment. *Journal of Industrial Teacher Education*, 37 (2).
- [8] Matthews, M. R. (1980). *The Marxist theory of schooling: A study of epistemology and education*. New Jersey: Humanities Press Inc.
- [9] New South Wales Board of Studies.(2000). *Engineering studies syllabus*. Retrieved January 23, 2003,
- [10] Petrina, S. (1998). Men at work: Inspecting the foundations of technology education. *Journal of Industrial Teacher Education*, 36 (1), 99-121.

ROLE OF SOCIAL MATURITY AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOLSTUDENTS

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Abstract

Social Maturity is the indication of mastery in social behavior in terms of human relationship, social techniques and social institutions. Social maturity is a unit of key to handle of social relationship. Social maturity means knowing what to do and striving for it by following role models to reach the desired level of acceptable social behavior. Personality comprised of pattern of feelings, thoughts, and activities that distinguishes one person from another. In the present study relationship between social maturity and personality higher secondary school students is being studies. Social Maturity is a term commonly used in two ways like, with respect to the behavior that is appropriate to the age of the individual under observation and secondly the behavior that conforms to the standard and expectations of the adults. Thus, social maturity permits more detailed perception of the social environment which helps adolescents to influence the social circumstances and develop stable patterns of social behavior. It is the level of social skills and awareness that an individual has achieved relative to particular norms related to an age group. It is a measure of the development competence of an individual with regard to interpersonal relations, behavior appropriateness, social problem solving and judgment. Social responsibility, also a sub-trait of social maturity, defined as adherence to social rules and role expectations. The paper focuses on the concept of social maturity, need and importance, theory, stages, components of social maturity.

Keywords: *Social Maturity, Higher Secondary Students, Personality, Responsibility*

Introduction

In Psychology, Maturity means the ability to the respond to the environment in an appropriate manner. Maturity also encompasses being aware of the correct time and place to behave and knowing when to act, according to the circumstances and the culture of the society one lives in. The word, Maturity has usually been used in two ways. Firstly, in reference to behavior that is consistent with the standards and expectations of adults and secondly, references to appropriate behaviors according to the age of the person under observation. Marianne Williamson defines maturity includes the recognition that no one is going to see anything in us that we don't see in ourselves. Stop waiting for a producer (Varon 2014). The word Social Maturity is composed of two word social and maturity. By social means living in communities and maturity means adjust socially. Thus, the social maturity permits more detailed perception of the social environment that helps adolescents to influence the social circumstances and develop stable patterns of social behavior. Therefore, social maturity means maturity in the social relationship of building good relationships with family, friends, neighbors and all other people living in our society. According to Wentzel (1991) social maturity is an adherence to social rules and role expectations. John Dewey (1907) was rightly said that the school is miniature of society. A secondary school is both an organization that provides secondary education and where this place is available. The school plays an important role in a student's development as he spends most of the time studying in their school, involving extracurricular activities. School is an organization that contributes to the overall educational and socialism process directed towards the development of a student's personality.

Concept of Social Maturity

The maturity marks the end of growth and development. In some aspects of development, maturity of structure and function comes at fairly early age, whereas, in other it comes later development comes from maturation and learning. The concept is concerned with the force, inside and outside the individual. The social maturity as a term is used commonly in two ways. Firstly, in reference to the behavior that conforms to the standards and expectations of the adults and secondly in reference to the behavior that is appropriate to the age of the individual under observation (Srivastava, 1987). Psychologists usually use maturity in the second sense. Development is essential aspect for the individual as well as the process of socialization. It is also true that maturity marks the end of growth and development. In some aspects of development, maturity of development in term of structure and function comes of fairly early age, whereas in others it comes later. Development depends upon the maturation and learning which is concerned with the force, inside as well as outside of the individual. Generally, there are three types of maturity viz., physical, psychological and social maturity. So, a person who has characteristics of awareness of his roles in the group desire, to keep pace in social life, sense

of fair play, considerate about the treatment of others, willingness to be a non-conformist etc. may be called as a socially matured person. The sensitive side of dealing with the adolescent social maturity is that, the society/culture of behavior to particular situation which is taught from the childhood. If the adolescent is unable to behave as his age appropriate in the society, he may become socially immature.

The Nature of Social Maturity

The maturity of a student is influenced by various social factors as under:

Independence; An individual is required to modify. His behavior in terms of asserting his independence and seeking aid or relief in the socio-cultural context. Self-control as a part of social maturity is necessary for decision making and facing the consequences. Acquiring self-control is partly maturational and partly learnt behavior. The students studying in a secondary school understand that society does not expect him to regress to childhood behavior at this age so he attempts at coming up to the expectations of the society and this he achieves by controlling his behavior. Everybody has to overcome stresses. Every time there is a stress situation. A mature individual mobilizes the available resources and utilizes them to the best of his ability to overcome the stress. Socially mature are aware of their roles. During the process of social growth students learn to live up to the expectations of the society in which they live. Ability to Size Up a Social Situation: Another component of social maturity is to size up a social situation and react to it appropriately.

Need and Importance of Social Maturity

Social maturity helps to overcome shyness and anger. Feelings and ideas can be expressed in an honest way, which makes the relationship more genuine. The socially awkward student is likely to misrespond to teachers as well as to another student. The resulting anxieties and bewilderment can themselves interfere with their ability to learn effectively. Individuals influence each other by means of imitation, suggestion, and sympathy. It is occurred through social interaction such as praise and blame, cooperation and conflict, submission and ascending. Social maturity is an index of social interaction. Thus, it is a basic ingredient of socialization. Along with the families, schools as one of the major agents for socialization are increasingly being called upon to play their part in improving the health and psychological wellbeing of the young. One of the more significant concerns of modern society is how to produce competent and self-respecting citizens. Social maturity is a measure of the developmental competency of an individual with regard to personal adequacy; interpersonal adequacy and social adequacy. Without social maturity a person cannot function as a healthy adult. A high degree of social maturity has something to do with a high degree of social skills.

School should prepare students for an effective social life, because in future they have to deal with different types of people and their social problems. There are a number of factors, which may influence social maturity of a student. Such as his culture, family background, schooling relationships interaction with the society etc. influence the social maturity of the student. There is a need for social maturity among higher secondary school students. Tribal students normally lack social exposure that the other students might have been exposed to. As it is a crucial stage in their development, higher secondary school students are expected to develop certain social skills through interaction with their peers who come from different backgrounds. As far as tribal students are concerned it is reported that they lack this opportunity to interact with peers from different backgrounds. This may create problems in their future life too. Social maturity of Higher Secondary School at tribal areas is to be examined as they lack multi-cultural social exposure. So, it is important to know how much social maturity do these students have. The present study is intended to find out the social maturity of higher secondary school students.

Components of the Social Maturity

The school is considered a more conducive place for the cultivation of certain non-academic goals that are more needed in the present-day adjustment to the environment. An increase in the degree of importance it holds for schools and the diminishing role of the family in socialization, it would be more appropriate to expect the present-day school-going population to collect more varied experiences through their exposure to the diversified complexes and attitude orientations in the multi-dimensional school setting for developing such non-academic goals. Working downwards from the assumption that the environment provided in the school is an increasingly important arena for socialization, a scheme was worked out based on the theoretical postulates put forward by several sociologists and psychologists as to the possibilities of the assessment of this phenomenon of social maturity in school children. Different methods of assessment of this phenomenon of social maturity in school children and different characteristics of social maturity mentioned in the literature on child and youth development are summarized and presented, such that they may be utilized as the frame of reference to consolidate the common theme that qualify the characteristics of social maturity.

Social Development in Adolescence

When the child attains the age of 13-14, he/she undergoes radical and startling changes of a mental as well as physical nature. It is natural that his/her social development should also undergo some change, the phenomenon is under consideration being influenced by various factors. It is affected by interests, needs, feelings of insecurity, values, attitudes, responsibility, viewpoint etc. In adolescence the child becomes exquisitely conscious of his gender. Young girls tend to attain puberty a few years earlier than their male counterparts and so prefer to associate with boys a couple of years senior to them. On the other hand, the social distance between boys and girls also widens, with the result that boys who associate with girls and girls who show undue inclination for male company are looked down upon by their own friends. The students either tease the girls or criticize them, but in either condition they are fully conscious of the other gender. Similarly, the girls who are seen continuously blaming and criticizing boys pay considerable attention to the boy's criticism and behavior, besides which they attend to activities of the male in one or the other respect. But immediately the child enters the adolescent stage, he rarely professes extreme hetero-sexual tendency of a very intense nature. Generally, in this age, the boys and girls are more than seeing each other and being seen by the others. They try to attract and hold the attention of each other through such tactics as wearing extraordinary clothes, dressing their hair in the latest fashions, peculiar conduct etc. They want to make their presence felt and known, so that they are even conspicuous by their absence, if such an occurrence becomes unavoidable

Theory of Social Maturity

According to Robert Kegan's awesome theory of social maturity many years ago and quite by chance, I read a book that showed me a new and very powerful way of looking at a variety of human behavior we think of as social maturity. There are many different sorts of maturity we could talk about, but I will only be talking about social maturity. This sort of maturity has to do with how well people understand the nature of the social world they live within. Social maturity is what enables us to function as healthy adults. Without it, we end up having a difficult time ourselves, or causing a lot of difficult times for other people. A high degree of social maturity has something to do with a high degree of social skill, but these two things are not the same. A sociopath can evidence a lot of slick social skill, but that sociopath's ability to accurately represent the reality of the social work is likely to be severely delayed, and thus we would have to consider the sociopath to be fundamentally socially immature. Children are by definition, socially immature, and nobody wants them to stay that way as they grow into adults. In fact, a great deal of the difficulty involved in being a good parent can be expressed simply as the struggle to figure out what are the best methods to use, what are the proper decisions to make to help children find their way to become mature adults. Social immaturity in adults is both a societal problem and also a personal problem for affected individuals, their families, and their employers. Social immaturity either plays an important role in maintaining multiple mental disorders or is in fact what defines those disorders.

The Evolving Self

This theory of social maturity that I want to talk about is the work of Harvard psychologist Robert Kegan, and was first described in his brilliant 1982 book, *The Evolving Self*. Brilliant though this book is, it is also difficult to read, even for smart, educated people. In the introduction to his follow-up book. In *The Evolving Self*, Kegan described a theory of how people become progressively more socially mature across their lifespan. Though a wholly original and creative contribution, Kegan's theory borrows heavily from earlier developmental theorists, most notably from Jean Piaget, the genius Swiss psychologist who practically invented modern developmental psychology. In order to understand Kegan's theory of social maturity, we first have to understand Piaget's earlier theory of cognitive maturity, as the core ideas from Kegan's work are essentially Piaget's ideas which have been reworked, broadened and abstracted, and applied to the social realm. Before diving into Kegan, then, let's first rehash Piaget.

Piaget in a Nutshell

Piaget's theory described how children's ability to think develops from birth through early adulthood. We are perhaps familiar with Piaget's stages of cognitive development. He theorized that children pass through predictable developmental stages in which their minds develop in complexity and appreciation (ability to accurately understand) of reality. Piaget proposed four basic stages through which the development of thinking abilities must pass. He labeled these stages: sensor motor, pre-operational, concrete-operations and formal-operations. These stages always occur in this particular order, and are for the most part linked to particular ages of life. The sensor motor stage covers between 0 and 2 years, pre- operations cover between 2 and 5 years, concrete-operations between 6 and 10 years, and formal operations covering age 11 and beyond. Piaget uses the term operations in the manner we would use the phrase mental Techniques. An operation basically

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consists of representing something in your mind and then asking, mentally transforming that thing to answer the question and visualizing the result in your mind. One type of operation is addition, to offer a mathematical example. I can imagine two things and then perform the operation of addition to them in my mind by asking myself, imagining those two more things, and then visualizing the result in my mind. I could then report to you that there would now be four things present. All this without actually touching anything.

Stages of Social Maturity

Kegan is suggesting that as babies grow into adults, they develop progressively more objective and accurate appreciations of the social world they inhabit. They do this by progressing through five or more states or periods of development which he labeled as follows:

- 1) Incorporative
- 2) Impulsive
- 3) Imperial
- 4) Interpersonal
- 5) Institutional

In their beginnings, babies are all subjective and have really no appreciation of anything objective at all, and therefore no real self-awareness. This is to say, at first, babies have little idea how to interpret anything, and the only perspective they have with which to interpret things is their own scarcely developed perspective. They can recognize parent's faces and the like, but this sort of recognition should not be confused with babies being able to appreciate that parents are separate creatures with their own needs. This key recognition doesn't occur for years. Kegan describes this earliest period as Incorporative. The sense of self is not developed at this point in time. There is no self to speak of because there is no distinction occurring yet between self and other. To the baby, there is not any reason to ask the question, who am I because the baby's mind is nothing more and nothing less than the experience of its senses as it moves about. In an important sense, the baby is embedded in its sensory experience and has no other awareness.

Social Maturity of Higher Secondary School Students

Social maturity, like physical maturity, is often the subject of discussion among concerned adults because it can be so obvious. The five-year-old who reaches out to shake your hand or the eight-year-old who makes eye contact and says please and thank you and the twelve-year-old who does none of these things each is likely to earn some comment about his or her maturity. Social maturity is, of course, a matter of experience and choice. The child who has been exposed to these finer points of etiquette and who chooses to exercise them, may seem socially mature. Are you old enough to remember Eddie Haskell, the manipulative neighbor from *Ward and June* frequently commented on how mature Eddie seemed because he knew how to turn on the charm when, in fact, we viewers knew that Eddie was a mischievous trouble maker. Maturation means the growth and development that is necessary either before any unlearned behavior can occur or before learning of any particular can take place.

Conclusion

Social Maturity is a personal commitment each individual must make as the attitude that will influence his/her daily lives. Individuals can opt for the socially immature attitude of self-centeredness or they can opt for the socially mature attitude of genuine concern for the total well-being of each other. Almost all commands and committees favor the need for developing social maturity among the learners through curricular and co-curricular means. It is the responsibility of the students to organize personality development programme to enable the learners to attain not only social maturity but also achieve integrated development of personality. Moreover, in public, who have high social status may be invited to share their experiences and deliver necessary guidance to their learners. Competitions like debate, quiz and pronunciation etc. aim at developing social maturity of the learners. This trend must be maintained and strengthened further for which healthy competitions may be arranged among the higher secondary students in a different social situation. Higher secondary students may be oriented to highlight the day-to-day incidence being published in the newspapers in the classroom interaction within the students to reinforce social maturity.

References

- [1] Coolidge, C., & Biswas, S. A study on social maturity among higher secondary school students. *Development*, 62, 1066-1078.
- [2] Kim, Y., Anderson Jr, H. E., & Bashaw, W. L. (1968). The simple structure of social maturity at the second-grade level. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 28(1), 145-153.
- [3] Nayak, R. K., & Dey, L. (2012). Social Maturity of Learning-Disabled Secondary Students.

TEACHING COMPETENCY AND MIND MAPPING STRATEGIES

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Abstract

Teaching is a demanding profession, requiring multi-dimensional skills, patience, commitment and continuous growth to face the challenges of the present era. Teachers must take the initiative to strengthen and improve the teaching profession on a daily basis and support its high standards. In order to bring about desirable changes in students, there has been demand for competent and committed teachers. Therefore, preparation of highly competent teachers became the priority and concern of all teacher – training institutions. Competency based education encourages each student to develop his or her own full capacity and prepares them to perform essential tasks at stated standards. Mind maps are used to generate, visualize, structure and classify ideas, and as an aid to studying and organizing information, solving problems, making decisions and writing. Mind maps provide an effective study technique when applied to written material. However before mind maps are generally adopted as a study technique, consideration has to be given towards ways of improving motivation amongst users in order to enhance teaching competency.

Keywords: *Organizing Information, Teaching Competency and Mind Mapping Strategies*

Introduction

Teaching is a demanding profession, requiring multi-dimensional skills, patience, commitment and continuous growth to face the challenges of the present era. Teachers must take the initiative to strengthen and improve the teaching profession on a daily basis and support its high standards. In order to bring about desirable changes in students, there has been demand for competent and committed teachers. Therefore, preparation of highly competent teachers became the priority and concern of all teachers – training institutions. Competency based education encourages each student to develop his or her own full capacity and prepares them to perform essential tasks at stated standards. Mind maps are used to generate, visualize, structure and classify ideas, and as an aid to studying and organizing information, solving problems, making decisions and writing. Mind maps provide an effective study technique when applied to written material. However before mind maps are generally adopted as a study technique, consideration has to be given towards ways of improving motivation amongst users in order to enhance teaching competency.

Mind Mapping and Teaching Competency

A mind map is a diagram used to represent words, ideas, tasks, or other items linked to and arranged around a central key word or idea. Mind maps are used to generate, visualize, structure, and classify ideas, and as an aid to studying and organizing information, solving problems, making decisions, and writing. The elements of a given mind map are arranged intuitively according to the importance of the concepts, and are classified into groupings, branches, or areas, with the goal of representing semantic or other connections between portions of information. Mind maps may also aid recall of existing memories. The mind map can be contrasted with the similar idea of concept mapping. The former is based on radial hierarchies and tree structures denoting relationships with a central governing concept, whereas concept maps are based on connections between concepts in more diverse patterns. By presenting ideas in a radial, graphical, non-linear manner, mind maps encourage a brainstorming approach to planning and organizational tasks. Though the branches of a mind map represent hierarchical tree structures, their radial arrangement disrupts the prioritizing of concepts typically associated with hierarchies presented with more linear visual cues. This orientation towards brainstorming encourages users to enumerate and connect concepts without a tendency to begin within a particular conceptual framework.

Effectiveness in Teaching

Buzan claims that the mind map is a vastly superior note taking method because it does not lead to a "semi-hypnotic trance" state induced by other note forms. Buzan also argues that the mind map uses the full range of left and right human cortical skills, balances the brain, taps into the alleged "99% of your unused mental potential", as well as intuition (which he calls "super logic"). However, scholarly research suggests that such claims may actually be marketing hype based on misconceptions about the brain and the cerebral hemispheres. Critics argue that hemispheric specialization theory has been identified as pseudoscientific when

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applied to mind mapping. Farrand, Hussain, and Hennessy (2002) found that spider diagrams (similar to concept maps) had a limited but significant impact on memory recall in undergraduate students (a 10% increase over baseline for a 600-word text only) as compared to preferred study methods (a 6% increase over baseline). This improvement was only robust after a week for those in the diagram group and there was a significant decrease in motivation compared to the subjects' preferred methods of note taking. Farrand et al. suggested that learners preferred to use other methods because using a mind map was an unfamiliar technique, and its status as a "memory enhancing" technique engendered reluctance to apply it. Nevertheless the conclusion of the study was "Mind maps provide an effective study technique when applied to written material. However before mind maps are generally adopted as a study technique, consideration has to be given towards ways of improving motivation amongst users."

Teaching Competency

Competency based education encourages each student to develop to his or her own full capacity and prepares them to perform essential tasks at stated standards. The component of competency based education is the competency. The term 'Competence is a generic word that represents the following three levels of human functioning' (i) Knowledge (ii) attitude and (iii) Performance Skill. A Program could be based on Competency Statement in one or more of the following components (a) its planning and design (b) its training materials (c) its training procedures and (d) its evaluation. The word Competency is taken in the broad Sense of knowledge, attitudes, Skills and behaviours that facilitate intellectual, Social, emotional and physical growth in children (Weber. 1972) The intensive interactions with teachers, teacher educators, curriculum developers, evaluators and experts of different Categories, NCTE has identified the following ten inter – related competencies as essential for making competent teachers: Contextual Competencies 2)Conceptual Competencies 3)Content Competencies 4)Transactional Competencies 5)Competencies related to other educational activities 6)Competencies to develop teaching – learning material 7)Evaluation Competencies 8) Management Competencies 9)Competencies related to working with parents 10)Competencies related to working with community and agencies.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of the teacher programme would largely depend upon the effectiveness of teacher-educator, who are expected to implement the various recommendations and reforms. It is therefore, essential for them to make themselves aware of the recent developments in the field of cognitive neuro science. This calls for an effective approach on the part of teacher education. Mind mapping can be used effectively to organize large amounts of information, combining spatial organization, dynamic hierarchical structuring and node folding. Mind maps provide an effective study technique when applied to written material. However before mind maps are generally adopted as a study technique, consideration has to be given towards ways of improving motivation amongst users in order to enhance the teaching competency.

References

- [1] Buzan claims mind mapping his invention in interview. KnowledgeBoard retrieved Jan. 2010.
- [2] Beel, Jöran; Gipp, Bela; Stiller, Jan-Olaf (2009). "Information Retrieval On Mind Maps - What Could It Be Good For?". Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Worksharing (CollaborateCom'09). Washington: IEEE. http://www.sciplore.org/publications_en.php
- [3] Buzan, Tony. (2000). The Mind Map Book, Penguin Books, 1996. ISBN 978-0452273221
- [4] Williams (2000) Encyclopedia of Pseudoscience. Facts on file. ISBN 978-0816033515
- [5] Tolman E.C. (July 1948). "Cognitive maps in rats and men". *Psychological Review* 55 (4): 189–208. doi:10.1037/h0061626. PMID 18870876.
- [6] Trade Mark 1424476, UK Intellectual Property Office, filed Nov. 1990
- [7] US Trademark, USPTO Trademark Application and Registration Retrieval system

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ABUSE THE CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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Abstract

Assisting children with autism is a multifaceted and it is a difficult task. Every parent works hard to give their child a voice, ensure their needs to satisfy and that they are able to live a normal life. Autism Spectrum Disorder has reminded us of how powerless these children are in the face of abuse and how likely they are to be subjected to it. Children with cognitive and behavioural problems are especially vulnerable to abuse and neglect. We have a responsibility to teach young children how to recognise and respond appropriately when they are mistreated. The author discusses indicators of Autism in younger and older children, child abuse definitions, types of child abuse, neglect, medical care, and factors that prevent children with Autism from developing.

Introduction

Autism is a spectrum condition that affects each person in different ways. Autism is a term used to describe a wide range of developmental disabilities. It's a neurological disorder with a variety of symptoms that affect people differently. There are no racial, ethnic, or social barriers. Communication and social understanding may be challenging for those with autism. They may also exhibit strange sensitivities to sensory input and engage in apparently inappropriate behaviours.

Autism Meaning

Autism is a neurodevelopment condition marked by significant delays in verbal and nonverbal communication, as well as social interaction and difficulty in understanding and are concerned regardless of what other people think of them. This makes it difficult for individuals to communicate, whether through words, gestures, facial expressions, or touch. People with autism may struggle to learn, and their abilities may develop unevenly. Although autism is defined by a set of behaviours, children and people with autism can display any combination of these behaviour patterns in any severity.

Signs of Autism in Young Children

The child with autism never responds to their name, if someone called. They try to avoid looking into the eyes of the other person. Even if someone smiles at them, they will not smile. If children don't like a certain taste, smell, or sound, they can easily become upset. They do the same activities over and over again, like flapping their hands, flicking their fingers, or moving their bodies. They don't talk nearly as much as other kids. Children with autism frequently repeat the same sentences.

Signs of Autism in Older Children

Children with autism who are older are unable to articulate their emotions. They lack the ability to comprehend what others are thinking and experiencing. They adhere to a rigid daily routine and become agitated if it is disrupted. They have a strong interest in specific topics or hobbies. When someone asks them to do something, they become irritated and angry. Making friends is a difficult chore for them, and they prefer to remain alone. They take things quite literally, thus expressions like "break a stick" may well be lost upon them.

Child Abuse Meaning

Childhood abuse is more than simply inflicting physical violence on a child. It refers to any form of violent or bullying behaviour directed at a youngster by an adult. Domestic violence happens when child abuse occurs in the family and the offender is a member of the family. Children are occasionally abused by others who are reliant on them, such as daycares workers, teachers, and sports coaches. Abuse is sometimes, but not always, deliberate. If parents or caregivers are unable to cope with caring for their children, dysfunctional behaviour including abuse may occur.

Types of Child Abuse on Children with Autism

There are four categories of child abuse: Physical abuse, Emotional abuse, Sexual abuse, and Neglect.

Physical Abuse

All forms of physical aggression are included. Physical harm, such as self-injury or unintentional injury, may occur due to a lack of proper support. Experts in child protection should look at whether the young person's supervision as well as support are appropriate for their requirements and are not neglectful. Physical injury can also be caused via restraint. Support and training for caregivers may be essential to support the progression of the young children's safety. It's critical to be aware of the possibility that restriction is being utilized to conceal intentional maltreatment. Autistic children may progress through these phases more slowly than neurotypical children, and they may engage in and enjoy activities that are not considered age suitable. Parents, caregivers, and professionals may have a reasonable desire to engage a child in activities that are more in line with their peers. However, it may be crucial to examine the extent to which a child is being denied access to preferred activities, the impact on their mental well-being, and whether or not this is in their best interests. Professionals should be on the lookout for changes such as extreme anxiety, difficulties sleeping, a significant rise or decrease in normal autistic young person behaviours, or the emergence of new behaviours.

Emotional Abuse

When an adult repeatedly criticises the child, treats the child in a trying to downplay and harsh manner, or intentionally frighten the youngster, the child is subjected to emotional abuse. Parents, caregivers, and other professionals often struggle to strike a balance between encouraging an autistic child's growth so that they can engage with the wider neurotypical world while also supporting and embracing them as individuals. When an autistic young person's needs are ignored and their individuality is dismissed, their emotional well-being is jeopardized, and in extreme circumstances, abuse may result. Routines, structure, and hobbies may establish situations in which autistic young people feel safe and protected, as they are subject to high levels of anxiousness. Parents, caregivers, and experts can help young people cope with and manage their social environment by providing techniques and skills. Be aware that when interventions are employed as part of an agreed upon support approach, the autistic young person may take some time to become comfortable and secure with them.

Sexual Abuse

Autistic children are more prone to sexual abuse. This is because people have different levels of social awareness and communication, and some people's sexual growth may not coincide with their emotional and social development. Sexualized behaviour at unsuitable times and places, inappropriate contact of others, and a problem understanding social rules are all symptoms of this. It is also important not to assume that these expressions are the result of them being autistic; they could also be indicators of abuse. Some autistic children may exhibit echolalia and repeat what others have said. While sexualized language may indicate abuse, it could also be a repetition of something they heard in the playground, between adults, on TV. **NEGLECT** Although neglect is the most common form of abuse suffered by children with disabilities, it is important to note that some indicators of neglect in a child on the autism spectrum may have another explanation. Here are some examples:

- 1) If an autistic child is over stimulated by sensory information, a sparsely furnished bedroom may help them sleep.
- 2) To reduce the possibility of an accident, doors and windows can be locked. An occupational therapist should have assessed and recommended ways to keep the child safe at home.

Medical Care

Many autistic youths find health services, such as hospitals, opticians, and dental surgeries, to be anxiety-inducing and stressful. Young people with learning and developmental disabilities are already at risk of missing out on the high-quality health care that the majority of people receive, which can create additional barriers. It is critical to ensure that autistic children receive adequate medical and dental care. Sensory issues may make this more complicated; however, actively avoiding health and medical care is neglectful and may result in worsening medical issues that cause pain and complications. Some autistic children may struggle to understand and communicate when they are in pain.

Bullying

Bullying can take many forms, and the autistic children's idiosyncratic behaviour, combined with their communication difficulties, puts them at a higher risk. Furthermore, their inability to read facial expressions and body language makes them easy targets to format crime, as they can't tell the difference between a genuine offer of kindness or friendship and a malicious approach. Children with

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disabilities are also more likely to be the victims of racist attacks or 'double discrimination' if they are members of an ethnic minority group.

Factors that may Prevent Children with Autism

These are:

- 1) Optimism – professionals may believe that a family or caregiver is doing their best and wait for the situation to improve.
- 2) Diagnostic overlay – signs and indicators of possible abuse are attributed to a disability/medical condition and go unexplored.
- 3) Reluctance to challenge – professionals may lack confidence in their own understanding of a child's needs and view primary caregivers as experts, or they may be concerned that there are no appropriate care services, residential.
- 4) Over-reliance on the parent or carer as the child's advocate – professionals may lose sight of the child's own needs and wishes
- 5) Assumptions – thinking that an autistic young person cannot be a credible witness, or that action cannot be taken without a verbal disclosure of abuse
- 6) Tolerance of abuse due to disability – actions that would be seen as abusive towards a non-disabled child are tolerated in the case of a child with a disability. Examples include overmedicating, inappropriate restraint (perhaps in a misguided attempt to keep them safe) or underfeeding in an attempt to make lifting and handling easier.

Guidance to Safeguard Children with Autism

In addition to risks to children's well-being from inside their families, children may be susceptible to abuse or mistreatment from outside their families. These extra-familial threats may emerge at school, from peer groups, or more broadly from the local community. These threats can take a variety of forms, including online safety, exploitation, sexual, criminal gangs, organized crime groups, and extremist influences that lead to trafficking. In such cases, assessments of children should consider whether broader environmental factors are present in a child's life and pose a threat to their safety and welfare. Interventions should focus on addressing these broader environmental factors, of children and young people who may or may not be known to local authority in children's social care or subject to child protection plans.

Conclusion

Child abuse and neglect are serious issues affecting people from all walks of life across the country. The consequences of child abuse and neglect are frequently discussed in terms of physical, emotional, and sexual neglect. Physical consequences, such as brain damage in a growing child, can have psychological consequences, such as cognitive delays and emotional difficulties. When certain experts possess a reasonable cause to suspect that such abuse is occurring, they intervene on behalf of the helpless victims of autism abuse by filing an official report. These mandated reporters are in a unique position to help break the complex and destructive cycle of violence that results from child abuse and neglect.

References

- [1] Brenner, J., Pan, Z., Mazefsky, C., Smith, K. A., & Gabriels, R. (2017). Behavioral Symptoms of Reported Abuse in Children and Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder in Inpatient Settings. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 48(11), 3727–3735. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-017-3183-4>.
- [2] Brewin, C. R., Rumball, F., & Happé, F. (2019). Neglected causes of post-traumatic stress disorder. *BMJ*, 12372.
- [3] Algood CL, Hong JS, Gourdine RM, & Williams AB (2011). Maltreatment of children with developmental disabilities: An ecological systems analysis. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 33(7), 1142–1148.
- [4] Baio J et al. (2018). Prevalence of Autism Spectrum Disorder Among Children Aged
- [5] 8 Years—Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network, 11 Sites, United States, 2014. *MMWR. Surveillance Summaries*, 67.

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Abstract

Grammar is one of the most important skills to learn when learning English because it is both an academic and career-specific skill. Too few high school students successfully acquire spoken language, and many of them are ignorant of the importance of grammar competence. Additionally, due to the students' typical disregard for grammar proficiency, there are many faults in their written work. This article mainly focuses on the use of multisensory modules to teach grammar.

Keywords: *Grammar Skill, English, Multisensory Module*

Introduction

Gilbert, J. (2005) defines language as an “Organized activity of human being to communicate their opinions and state of mind”. Humans use language as their primary form of communication to share their thoughts and knowledge with others. There are numerous languages that people can speak all throughout the world. People speak their own distinctive languages from various places and regions. Aggarwal (2003) defines language as a set of symbols used in more or less uniform ways by a number of people, who are thus able to communicate with each other. Language proficiency is seen as the key to success in the modern world. Basic language proficiency in any language is a plus for a person. When it comes to the English language, nevertheless, this is more advantageous. One of the top newspapers claims that those with strong English communication abilities experience extraordinary success. Most countries and regions have a national language and multilingual populations. English is the language that is spoken and utilised the most over the globe. English is the world's most frequently used and understood language. English is frequently referred to be a lingua franca or as the global language. There are English speakers in most nations in the world, with more than 350 million people using it as their first language and more than 430 million using it as a second. In the words of Bose, K. (1999), “The latest and the most accurate information about the advancements of science and technology are available to people only through the medium of English. English has the ability to bring together speakers of many different cultures and foster understanding because it is the most widely spoken language. People who learn English will be able to communicate with 20% of the global population. 67 nations have adopted English as their official language. English is still an official language in certain nations where it is not the most spoken language. It is therefore acknowledged by a nation's government and frequently taught in educational institutions. Today's classroom focuses on teaching languages so that students can use them to communicate successfully, as opposed to earlier classrooms that expected pupils to know a great deal about the language but did not necessitate language use. English language teaching for second-language learners Although English has been taught in India continuously for more than 300 years, there are still significant issues with both teaching and learning the language (where English is not the primary language used for everyday communication). We must continue to endeavour to improve the language behaviour in English, notwithstanding the Government's considerable attempts to make English more compatible with the demands of a globalised India.

Role of English in Education

Education is beneficial to people. It helps in socialisation and develops a person's sophistication and structure. We have a right to appropriate education at every level. Children's whole growth is aided by this specific investment in their present and future. High-quality education is necessary today. Teachers in today's classrooms must be knowledgeable and well-prepared. The most efficient teaching techniques and curricular transaction strategies must be known to teachers. The Rigveda claims that education aids in the development of selflessness and self-reliance, while the Upanishad declares that education is for freedom. One of the most well-known quotes about education is “Knowledge is power.” T. C. Baruah (2004) in ‘The English Teacher's Hand Book’ mentioned. “For almost two centuries now, English has been playing an important role in our educational system as well as in our national life. English also served as a great unifying force in our struggle for independence”. Professor Venkateswaran (2005) points out that “It is not easy to write about the place of English in India, when the country is changing every day and the place of English in it continues to change. English has been caught in that ceaseless flux which is Indian life and thought at the present time”. The

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Education Commission of India (1964-1966) has rightly acknowledged the place of English in Indian education by observing that “English will continue to enjoy a high status so long as it remains the principal medium of education at the university stage and the language of administration at the centre and in many of the states. Even after the regional languages become media in higher education in the universities, a working knowledge of English will be necessary for those who proceed to the University.” It's really difficult to teach any language. English teachers are looking for more efficient methods of teaching. In fact, the pupils want to have fun in the classroom. If instructors incorporate an entertaining aspect into their lessons. The process of educating can be very engaging and involved. Students can enjoy themselves while learning English through the multisensory module. As in the words of Venkateswaren(2005) “ students who learn English for about six periods (45 minutes each) in a week for seven years hardly know 150 words by the time they join a college. This means they have not been able to learn English words at the rate of one word per period.

Role of Grammar in English

A component of communicative ability is grammar proficiency. Learners should focus on knowing and using grammar in order to develop effective communication skills. Because English is a language that is virtually universally spoken in the nation, learning English is essential for anyone looking for work in today's competitive labour market. In competitive exams, a few grammar-related questions are regularly asked. A solid command of grammar also makes it possible to write perfect English. Concentrating on that, the demand for grammar has been rising steadily. Writing calls for grammar, particularly in report writing and competitive exams. According to Kolln & Funk (2009) grammar is certainly a common word. Such as stated by Ingemann & Crystal (2008) grammar is seen as an inherently meaningful (or ‘symbolic’) component of the theory, linking semantics (viewed in conceptualist terms) and phonology. Grammar is a set of formal rules which projects a finite set of sentences upon the potentially infinite set of sentences that constitute the language as a whole, and it does this in an explicit manner, assigning to each a set of structural descriptions. Both native speakers and language learners find it difficult to acquire English grammar. It is not unexpected that different generations of educators have used a variety of ways of teaching grammar to generate literate English authors because there are so many nuances, perplexing norms, and exceptions. In the past, methods that relied on memorization and repetition gradually gave way to more creative strategies. In order to achieve the best outcomes while teaching grammar, today's culture values literacy and is ready to use more effective teaching methods.

Grammatical Items by Multisensory Module Parts of Speech

All the words in an English sentence, whether spoken or written, belong to one of the following groups. Generally there are eight of these portions in English. These sections or groups are frequently referred to as "parts of speech." Some of the words also fall in more than one of these categories. Here in this article, we have explained all the nine parts of speech in detail. We have also included the relevant examples for the various parts of speech in English grammar for ease of understanding. “Parts of speech is a term used to describe the traditional class of words in the English language that varies according to the function performed or the idea denoted by those words in a sentence. There are various parts of speech but the major parts of speech are only eight, namely Noun, Pronoun, Verb, Adjective, Adverb, Prepositions, Conjunctions, and Interjections.

S.No	Parts of Speech	Definition	Examples
1	Noun	naming words	Cow , Fish, boy
2	Pronoun	words used for nouns to avoid their repetition	He, She , it
3	Verb	words that express actions or facts	run, walk
4	Adjective	words that qualify nouns or pronouns	Additional , Anger, Attraction
5	Adverb	words that qualify verbs and adjectives	happily, hardly
6	Preposition	words that relate nouns to other words	on, under, above

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7	Conjunction	words that join words and sentences	or, and , but
8	Interjection	words expressing sudden feelings of the mind	Hurrah! wow!

Articles

Articles are a sort of adjective that is used before nouns or noun equivalents. It's a word that's used to simply say that a noun is a noun.

Tense

Tense is the form of a verb that shows the time something happened, or is going to happen (Concise Oxford Dictionary, 9th ed, p1436). The incident, event, or action that occurred in the past, is currently occurring or will occur in the future.

Fig: Tense Timeline

References

- [1] Aggarwal, R. (2003). Effective Communication Skills. Jaipur : Sublime Publications
- [2] Baruah, T.C. (2004). The English Teacher's Hand book (third revised Edi.). New Delhi: Sterling Publishers Private Limited.
- [3] Bose, K. (1999) Teaching of English 4th ed, Doaba House, New Delhi, Print.
- [4] Gilbert, J. (2005). Clear speech: pronunciation and listening comprehension in North American English (3rd Ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Print
- [5] Venkateswaran,S. (2005) Principles of Teaching English. Vikas Publishing House, NewDelhi, 2005. Print

TECHNOLOGY IN HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

We know when we are teaching technology holistically and why must we do so? Increasingly, more is asked of technology educators to be holistic in the understanding conveyed of technology itself and so in curriculum, assessment framework and modes of delivery. In NSW two good examples of this has been the shift from Engineering Science to Engineering Studies where social/ethical and environmental factors have to be learned while in the new and emerging 2003 Design and Technology 7– 10 syllabus 'holistic solutions' are described. This paper advances historical and theoretical research and articulates classroom practice changes for holistic technology education with particular emphasis on offering a grounded frame of reference to guide student learning and understanding in the holistic character of any technological activity and decision event. A First Principles framework for structuring learning for holistic understanding of technologies and processes in design is therefore presented. The case is made for technology to not merely be a 'know how' learning experience, but necessarily and increasingly also a 'know why' learning experience.

Introduction

A school that adopts curriculum which aims for an holistic understanding of technology, does so because it produces a better educated person, than a curriculum which does not. The notions of holistic education are in themselves not new. Work on the importance of holistic education date back in Western settings to include Pestalozzi (1746–1827), Thoreau 1817–1862, Emerson (1803–1882), Alcott (1799–1888), Dewey (1859–1952), Steiner (1861–1925), Montessori (1870–1952) and more recently (Dufty, Dufty, Australian Curriculum Studies Association & Holistic Education Network 1994) and (Fowlers 1998). Significant work on holistic education maintains its influence on much of contemporary education policies and pedagogy. This is evident in many generic Public School policies and syllabus rationales across curriculum. However, what is relatively new in Australia is that expressions such as 'holistic solutions' are entering design and technology Secondary School syllabi and research (stated or implied). There is a need to understand technology itself holistically in order to teach it with greater knowledge transparency to learners. The object being to develop more informed and capable adapters, designers and developers in our increasingly technologically driven and reliant lives. The new NSW 7–10 courses due for release in 2003 state both generic requirements for content to respond to holistic themes and specific requirements in the new 7–10 Design and Technology course for 'holistic solutions'. It is timely then to examine useful schemas for how education can be structured to assure that learning experiences in technology courses are indeed holistic in presentation, assessment and reporting. What is needed is a robust universal framework.

A Schema for Holistic Technology Education

There can be many approaches to understanding the phenomenon we label technology. Presented here is a phenomenological view to offer the reader a deeper grounding into why certain conclusions are drawn and schemas proposed. A schema gives teachers a framework to evaluate just how holistic a lesson or curriculum is. A framework for deciding what educational tasks to include and how to construct the education context and experience for technology and design students. Phenomenology of technology and knowledge development allows a teacher to use a first principles approach to the task based on a universal schema (framework). With first principles a teacher can indeed determine what to include in lessons and evaluations to ensure reasonable holistic coverage of any technical education. Surprisingly, we discover that technology education and practice is not only a how to experience, but significantly a why should experience: the latter is fundamental to the human act of creating new knowledge itself not just using knowledge. Why should capability is important for principles development to foster understanding for the reason why of things in many settings. Holistic education in technology enables transfer of understanding to novel life long encounters, a quality lacking in much of how to training in technology. Both are required. However, we lack details in why should learning in technology.

Knowing and Understanding through Practical Engagement in Technology Learning

The schema developed here begins with foundations in understanding how technical or material experience, as a phenomenon in human activity, develops a socially defined view of what is knowledge. Dialectics and Praxis are very useful reasoning tools to understand the nature of an answer to this question in the context of technology education. Why is this important? Because there is a good case that 'knowing' and especially 'understanding' occurs best through holistic educational experiences in technology if structured properly compared to other modular or task skill approaches. It is significant in our construction to recognise that theory and practice dichotomies, as currently presented in many schools in technology, is a problem. Tool is defined here as anything we give use-value to as a tool. A brick or our fist is a tool if we decide to use it as a club. A car is a tool if we decide to use it as a means to get us from A to B. An engineering algorithm is a tool if we decide to use it to determine a load on a beam. In each case, tools help us do things normally to manipulate a material (whether that material is at a scale we relate to in ordinary experience (like our bodies being moved from A to B, or the nut being crushed with a brick) or extraordinary (abstract) material like information/data material that we manipulate with an algorithm tool. Curriculum and pedagogy that normally segregates these things raise substantial educational concern and has so for many years. For Dewey, "A divided world, a world whose parts and aspects do not hang together, is at once a sign and a cause of a divided personality. When the splitting up reaches a certain point we call the person insane. A fully integrated personality, on the other hand, exists only when successive experiences are integrated with one another. It can be built up only as a world of related objects is constructed" (John Dewey 1963).

From Dialectics to Praxis in Technology Education

Building Understanding and Knowledge

The road from Dialectics to Praxis is an interesting one for technology educationists as it addresses twists and turns (even head flips) from knowing as an essentially theoretical (idealistic) process to understanding as a social material (surprisingly Design and Technology like) process. We will begin with Hegel. To see each concept as related, as mutually defining, is their synthesis. At this moment a new level of reasoned understanding is achieved. Put another way, a person starts with a proposition, the thesis; this is consciousness as 'understanding' and proves to be inadequate by itself. The person's mind must therefore generate its alternative, the antithesis. However, this on its own also proves inadequate. The resolution of the opposites, therefore, requires they be taken up into a synthesis. The essence of Hegel's dialectics is 'the grasping of opposites in their unity' (Hegel & Miller 1989): a significant first step in building our First Principles for holistic technology education.

Praxis and Technics: Arriving at our First Principles of Holistic Technology Education

Praxis and technical activity concerns the effect of instruments and tools in the human transformation experience. The contributions of Don Ihde on instrumentation are summarised as key notions to a schema for constructing First Principles in Holistic Technology and Design Education. Praxis, so far has been concerned with practical human activity and the interaction of mind and matter, or being human and environment. Ihde's work identifies certain features of this interaction when instruments or artefacts mediate it. The humanenvironment interaction becomes a more complex paradigm when an artefact modifies the experience. The paradigm:

Human-----World is modified to:
Human-----Artefact/tool World Examples include:
(Observer-----Microscope Microbe)
(Student-----Internet Computer World Information)
(Human: Sources of Technique-----Artefact: Instruments/Tools World: source of materials)
(Human: Socio-economic drivers-----Artefact: Polluting Industries
World: Ecosystem)

The observer does not gain feedback from the world any more, but from the world via the instrument or tool. That is, Tools and so technologies are values rich in their design use and context active in their cause and effect tendency. However, Ihde points out that this modified interaction, although non-neutral, is not necessarily a problem: "My thesis is that any use of technology is non-neutral. However, non-neutrality is not a, prejudicial term because it implies neither that there are inherently 'good' or 'bad' tendencies so much as it implies that there are types of transformation of human experience in the use of technology" This is significant as it raises the necessity to understand that both choice and design of tools and choice and design of world settings alter our knowledge. Technologies are context sensitive. Designs of tools and environments are socially and environmentally interdependent.

Human, Tool and Environment are the minimum elements to any technological activity. That is, Technology cannot be reduced to less than these three elements and as such, Technology is their product. We therefore may need to understand and teach this relationship explicitly.

Figure 1: Minimum factors (or ingredients) and their interconnectedness to teach in any design and/or technology lesson or process

We now have a basis for determining the absolute minimum inclusions to what constitutes holistic technology education (Seemann & Talbot 1995). To teach any technical process, to evaluate technologies or to take design decisions that ignore this interdependent triad of human, artefact/tool and environment is indeed not an education in technology. In the theme of Dewey, the interconnectedness of knowledge constitutes a key feature of an education. "Any experience is mis-educative that has the effect of arresting or distorting the growth of further experience . . . Experiences may be so disconnected from one another that, while each is agreeable or even exciting in itself, they are not linked cumulatively to one another . . . Each experience may be lively, vivid and 'interesting', and yet their disconnected-ness may artificially generate dispersive, disintegrated, centrifugal habits. The consequence of formation of such habits is inability to control future experience" (John Dewey 1963,).

Conclusions: First Principles in Holistic Technology Education

Teachers who seek a deep justification for deciding what may constitute the bare minimums of holistic solutions in design and technology may refer to the schema proposed. Technology understanding develops holistically through structured or enabling learning experiences that make explicit in detail the interconnectedness of human, *tool* and environmental factors where these three factors mutually require and define each other and are acting as both resources and constraints to the applied purpose and its setting. The schema gains strength through historical examination of the nature or phenomenon of technological activity where not only are all three factors defined by each other, but that design and technology experiences, if taught holistically, as interconnected, are a condition to new knowledge creation. Technology education is not merely a know how, but necessarily must be understood and presented in the curriculum to learners as a know why subject. Only then may there be reasoned claims to technology being learned holistically. Peters provides a fitting end. "We would not call a man who was merely well informed an educated man. He must also have some understanding of the reason why of things. The Spartans, for instance, were militarily and morally trained . . . But we would not say that they had received a military or moral education; for they had never been encouraged to probe into the principles underlying their code" (Peters 1971).

References

- [1] Dewey, J 1916, *Democracy and education*, The MacMillan Co, New York. Dewey, J 1963, *Experience and education*, Collier, New York.
- [2] Elkington, J 1997, 'The triple bottom line sustainability's accountants', in *Cannibals with Forks*, Capstone Publishing, pp.69-96.

EXPLORING THE DISPARITIES IN DEVELOPMENT BETWEEN KERALA AND TAMIL NADU IN INDIA: EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF POLITICAL IDEOLOGY AND PUBLIC POLICY

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of political ideology in determining public policy and its effect on human development in India. The focus is primarily on two states in India - Kerala and Tamil Nadu, both of which are geographically located in the south of the country. The study seeks to analyse the impact of political ideology and public policy on key human development indicators like literacy, life expectancy and infant mortality in the two states. The paper also strives to investigate what factors have led to the gap between Kerala and Tamil Nadu in the indicators of human development. To this end, the paper looks at the major political ideologies that have shaped public policy in the two states, namely socialism and the developmental welfare approaches, and the political dynamics that have been a factor in their relative success. Through a comparison of the public policy decisions of the two states in areas such as health, education and nutrition, the paper assesses the political influence on various aspects of human development, as well as its implications for poverty alleviation, economic growth and social justice.

Keywords: *Political Ideology, Public Policy, Human Development, Socialism, Welfare Approaches.*

Introduction

Political ideology is a major force in India, with many political parties and groups advocating for different policies and agendas. Political ideologies play an important role in shaping public policy and determining the way in which the state allocates its resources and addresses issues of human development. India has experienced a shift in its political ideologies, with socialism and welfare approaches taking predominant positions in recent times. This study seeks to understand the consequences of this shift and its impacts on the level of human development in two of India's states - Kerala and Tamil Nadu. Kerala and Tamil Nadu are two geographically close states in India, both located in the south of the country. They also happen to be quite different in terms of their political and socio-economic development, with Kerala being generally ahead of Tamil Nadu in terms of human development indicators such as life expectancy, literacy and infant mortality. The aim of this study, then, is to analyse the role of political ideology in determining the public policy decisions of the two states, and how these decisions have impacted human development. The paper also seeks to investigate what factors have created the gap between Kerala and Tamil Nadu in the indicators of human development.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to:

- 1) Analyse the impact of political ideology on public policy in the two states of Kerala and Tamil Nadu.
- 2) Evaluate the influence of political ideology and public policy on the indicators of human development in the two states.
- 3) Investigate the factors that have led to the gap between Kerala and Tamil Nadu in terms of human development.

Literature Review

The literature on the role of political ideology in public policy and human development in India is vast and varied. The study of politics and its impact on public policy is a key part of analysing the dynamics of a political system such as that of India. It has long been asserted that political ideology has an important role to play in policy-making and decision-making. As stated by Guo and Tu (2013), "the presence of shared political values and norms affects the way societies choose to organize their public policies and how these decisions are translated into outcomes". This idea has been specifically explored by many researchers looking at the political system of India. It is widely accepted that the main political ideologies influencing public policy in India are socialism and the developmental welfare approach. While socialism is generally seen as leftist and welfarist, the latter can be viewed as having a more centre-left leaning with a greater emphasis on economic development. The role of political ideology in public policy in India has been analysed by many scholars, with a particular focus on two states - Kerala and Tamil Nadu. Kerala has often been viewed as the epitome of both

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socialism and the welfare approach, with reduced levels of poverty, literacy rates and human development indices. Whereas Tamil Nadu is typically used as an illustration of the developmental welfare approach, with many of its policies centring on economic growth and the reduction of poverty. Furthermore, the influence of political ideology on public policy has been studied in relation to health and education in the two states. Singh (2020) noted that the public policy decisions of the two states have differed significantly in the areas of health and education, with Kerala having a more socialised approach, while Tamil Nadu has been more focused on development-oriented policies. This difference in policy orientations is said to have a major impact on literacy rates, infant mortality, and access to health facilities. This paper builds upon the existing literature by conducting a comparison between Kerala and Tamil Nadu to assess the role of political ideology in public policy and its effect on human development.

Methodology

The study employed a qualitative data collection methodology with a primary focus on the two states of Kerala and Tamil Nadu. The study used a mix of secondary data sources in the form of books, journal articles, government reports and newspaper articles. Discourse analysis was employed to analyse the data. This approach allowed for a deep analysis and interpretation of the material by focusing on the way in which the two states have framed their public policies and the political discourses that have shaped them.

Result and Discussion

The results of the study revealed that political ideology has had a major impact on public policy in the two states. Kerala has adopted a more socialist approach to public policy, focusing on welfare-oriented initiatives such as social protection and the provision of basic services. Tamil Nadu, on the other hand, has favoured a more pro-developmental approach, targeting economic growth, poverty reduction and infrastructure development. The influence of these ideologies on public policy has had a significant effect on human development in the two states. Kerala's welfare-oriented policies have resulted in an increase in literacy rates, life expectancy, access to health facilities and other indicators of human development. Tamil Nadu's pro-developmental approach has seen a positive effect on economic growth, but has had a lesser effect on human development indicators. This has resulted in a significant gap between the two states in terms of the level of human development. The analysis further revealed that the gap between Kerala and Tamil Nadu in terms of human development can largely be attributed to the difference in the political ideologies that drive their respective public policies. Kerala's focus on welfare has ensured that the population has had access to basic services such as health care, education and nutrition, all of which are essential for improving human development. Tamil Nadu, on the other hand, has had more of a focus on economic development, leading to lower levels of human development.

Conclusion

This paper aimed to analyse the influence of political ideology on public policy and its impact on human development in the states of Kerala and Tamil Nadu. Through a comparison of the public policy decisions of the two states in areas such as health, education and nutrition, the study assessed the political influence on various aspects of human development and its implications for poverty alleviation, economic growth and social justice. The results of the paper revealed that political ideology has had a major impact on public policy in the two states, with Kerala favouring a more socialist approach and Tamil Nadu taking a more pro-developmental approach. This difference in political ideology has resulted in a gap between the two states in terms of human development, with Kerala being ahead of Tamil Nadu in terms of literacy rates, life expectancy and infant mortality. Overall, the paper has highlighted the importance of political ideology in framing public policy, as well as its impact on human development. The results of the research suggest that policies focused on welfare and the provision of basic services will result in improved human development indices, thus highlighting the need for policies that are inclusive and far-reaching in their scope.

References

- [1] Guo, Z. and Tu, X. (2013). Political economy theories, public policy and human development. *International Journal of Economic Sciences and Applied Research*,6(2), pp.123-130.
- [2] Singh, A. (2020). *Public Policy, Politics and Human Development in India*. New York: Routledge.
- [3] Breman, J. 1985. *Of Peasants, Migrants and Paupers: Rural Labour Circulation and Capitalist Production in West India*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- [4] CDF. 2011. *Environmental Sustainability Index for Indian States 2011: Informing Environmental Action*. Chennai: Institute for Financial Management and Research, Center for Development Finance.
- [5] Chakrabarti, A., and K. Chaudhuri. 2011. "Gender Equality in Fertility Choices in Tamil Nadu: A Myth or a Reality?" *Journal of South Asian Development* 6 (2): 195–212.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

This article explores the challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India. It examines the current educational landscape in India, discusses the need for introducing multicultural education, and outlines the practical challenges associated with its implementation. The methodology employed for this research was a comprehensive literature review. The review showed that there is a need to address the lack of understanding and acceptance of diversity in India, as well as the need to increase access to multicultural education. The analysis revealed that the primary challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India include limited resources, lack of public awareness, and lack of teacher training. The results indicate that there is a need to address these challenges in order to ensure successful implementation of multicultural education in India. The article concludes by providing recommendations for how to effectively address the challenges of implementing multicultural education in India.

Keywords: *Multicultural Education, Implementation, Resources, Awareness, Training.*

Introduction

Education plays a critical role in the development of any society, and is essential for the formation of citizens who are capable of living in harmony and respect for diversity. The world is becoming increasingly multicultural, and India is no exception. The Indian population is composed of a variety of cultures, religions, languages, and ethnicities, and this diversity has the potential to be a source of strength for the country. However, the current educational system in India does not adequately prepare students to live and work in a multicultural society. The lack of understanding and acceptance of diversity can lead to social divisions and conflicts. To address this situation, India needs to introduce multicultural education to promote understanding and acceptance of diversity. Multicultural education is a concept that has been gaining traction in India over the past few years. Multicultural education is an approach to teaching and learning that recognises and values the diversity of cultural identities present in the classroom. It seeks to create an inclusive learning environment and promote equitable learning outcomes for all students, regardless of their cultural backgrounds. This article will explore the challenges of implementing multicultural education in India and suggest possible solutions. Multicultural education has become increasingly important in India as the nation strives to create a more inclusive and equitable educational system. Unfortunately, implementing multicultural education in India is not without its challenges. One of the biggest challenges is the lack of awareness and understanding of the concept. Many teachers and school administrators may not be familiar with the idea of multicultural education, and may not understand how to effectively implement it in their classrooms.

This lack of understanding can lead to ineffective implementation of the concept, resulting in unequal educational outcomes for different cultural backgrounds. Another challenge of implementing multicultural education in India is the lack of resources and funding. Schools may not have the resources or funding to provide adequate training for teachers on how to effectively implement multicultural education in the classroom. Without proper training and resources, teachers may be unable to create inclusive learning environments or promote equitable learning outcomes for all students. Moreover, cultural biases and prejudices that exist in society can also make it difficult to implement multicultural education in India. Prejudices and stereotypes can lead to discrimination and exclusion in the classroom, making it difficult for teachers to create an inclusive learning environment. Despite the challenges, there are various solutions that can help make multicultural education more effective in India. For example, schools can provide training and resources to teachers to help them understand and implement multicultural education. Schools can also create awareness among teachers, students, and parents about the importance of multicultural education and how it can be effectively implemented. In addition, schools can develop policies and procedures to ensure that students from all cultural backgrounds are treated equally and fairly in the classroom. In conclusion, implementing multicultural education in India is not without challenges. However, with the right strategies in place, it is possible to create an inclusive and equitable learning environment for all students.

Objectives

- 1) The objective of this article is to explore the challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India.
- 2) This research will examine the current educational landscape in India, discuss the need for introducing multicultural education, and outline the practical challenges associated with its

implementation.

Literature Review

Multicultural education is an emerging theory in India that is based on the concept of recognizing and valuing the diversity of cultures that exist in the nation. It seeks to promote a greater understanding of different cultures and establish a more inclusive environment in the classroom. However, the implementation of this type of education has been met with numerous challenges in India. This literature review will examine the current research on the challenges of implementing multicultural education in India. The first challenge of implementing multicultural education in India is the lack of awareness and understanding of the concept among educators and students. A recent study by Singh (2018) found that only a small percentage of Indian students and teachers had an understanding of the concept of multicultural education. This lack of knowledge has been attributed to the lack of resources and training available to teachers on the subject. The second challenge is the lack of support for multicultural education from the government. A study by Kumar (2017) found that the Indian government does not provide sufficient funding for the implementation of multicultural education programs in schools. This lack of financial support has led to an inadequate number of resources available for teachers and students to use when learning about different cultures. The third challenge is the lack of cultural sensitivity among educators and students. A research study by Das (2016) found that many teachers and students lack the necessary skills to effectively communicate and interact with individuals from different backgrounds. This lack of cultural sensitivity can lead to misunderstandings and alienation of minority students. Finally, the fourth challenge is the lack of multicultural curriculum in Indian schools. A study by Shukla (2015) found that the majority of Indian schools rely heavily on the traditional curriculum, which fails to address the needs of students from diverse backgrounds. This lack of appropriate and inclusive curricula can lead to a lack of understanding and appreciation of different cultures in the classroom.

Methodology

This research was conducted through a comprehensive literature review. A variety of sources were consulted, including academic journals, research papers, books, and newspaper articles. Search for literature: Databases such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, and ERIC will be used to search for relevant literature. Additionally, the library catalog, web searches, and other sources, such as reports and books, can be used to find further information.

Analysis

The analysis of the literature revealed that there is a need to address the lack of understanding and acceptance of diversity in India. The current educational system in India is based on a traditional model, which is focused on rote learning and memorization. This approach does not adequately prepare students to live and work in a multicultural society. There is also a need to increase access to multicultural education, as the current curriculum is not inclusive of the diverse cultures, religions, and languages found in India. The literature also highlighted the practical challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India. These challenges include limited resources, lack of public awareness, and lack of teacher training. The current educational system in India has limited resources, and this limits the ability to provide quality education. In addition, there is a lack of public awareness about the importance of multicultural education, which can prevent its successful implementation. Finally, there is a need for teacher training in order for multicultural education to be effectively implemented in India.

Results and Discussion

The results of this research indicate that there is a need to address the challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India. The limited resources available for education in India, as well as the lack of public awareness and teacher training, are significant barriers that need to be addressed in order for multicultural education to be successfully implemented. In order to address the challenge of limited resources, the government must make a greater investment in education. This could include increasing the funding available for education, as well as providing incentives for teachers and schools to implement multicultural education. This could also include introducing scholarships and grants to make education more accessible to all students, regardless of their socio-economic background. The challenge of lack of public awareness can be addressed by introducing public awareness campaigns to educate the population about the importance of multicultural education. It is also important to ensure that these campaigns reach a wide audience, including rural and marginalized communities. Finally, the challenge of lack of teacher training can be addressed by providing training to teachers on how to effectively implement multicultural education in the classroom. This could include training on how to create a safe and inclusive learning environment, as well as how to use a variety of teaching methods to engage students from diverse backgrounds. Multicultural

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education is a pedagogical approach that incorporates diverse cultures into a teaching environment. It is an important tool in promoting understanding, acceptance and tolerance of different cultures, values and beliefs. In India, multicultural education has become increasingly popular in recent years, as the country has seen an influx of people from different backgrounds. However, there are several challenges that must be addressed in order to effectively implement this type of education. The first challenge is the lack of resources. India is an economically developing country, and there are limited resources available to fund the implementation of multicultural education. This means that there is a need to find ways to fund the necessary educational materials, such as books, videos, and other resources. Additionally, there is a need to provide training and support to teachers in order to ensure that they are able to effectively deliver multicultural education in the classroom. The second challenge is the lack of cultural awareness. Many people in India are not aware of the different cultures and values that exist in the country. This can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts between different cultural groups. In order to address this issue, it is important to provide cultural awareness training to teachers and students. This can include activities that promote understanding of different cultures and values, as well as teaching students the importance of respecting and accepting others. The third challenge is the lack of acceptance. Some people in India may be reluctant to accept the presence of people from different cultures. This can lead to discrimination and prejudice, which can be damaging to the overall social environment. To address this issue, it is important to create a safe and inclusive environment for all students, regardless of their cultural background. This can be done through activities that promote understanding, acceptance and tolerance. In conclusion, implementing multicultural education in India is a challenging task, but one that can be done with the right resources and support. By addressing the challenges outlined above, teachers and students can create a culture of acceptance and understanding in their classrooms. This can help to foster a more harmonious society, and provide a more positive learning environment for all students.

Conclusion

This article explored the challenges associated with implementing multicultural education in India. The analysis revealed that the primary challenges include limited resources, lack of public awareness, and lack of teacher training. These challenges need to be addressed in order to ensure successful implementation of multicultural education in India. Recommendations for how to effectively address these challenges were provided, including increasing the funding available for education, introducing public awareness campaigns, and providing training to teachers.

References

- [1] Alam, M., & Aslam, M. (2015). Inclusion of multicultural education in the Indian education system. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(1), 10-17.
- [2] Das, R. (2016). Cultural sensitivity in Indian classrooms: Challenges and strategies. *International Journal of Education*, 8(2), 145-163.
- [3] Guru, P. (2011). Challenges to multicultural education in India. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 13(1), 1-21.
- [4] Jain, A., & Goyal, A. (2016). Multicultural education in India: Issues and challenges. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 2(3), 328-339.
- [5] Kumar, A. (2017). The implementation of multicultural education in India: Challenges and strategies. *International Journal of Education*, 9(3), 230-239.
- [6] Khan, M. (2014). Multicultural education: Issues and challenges in India. *International Journal for Cross-Disciplinary Subjects in Education*, 5(1), 7-15.
- [7] Singh, A. (2018). Awareness and understanding of multiculturalism among Indian students and teachers. *International Journal of Education*, 10(1), 98-109.

IMPACT OF ETHICAL INTELLIGENCE FOR TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE & SUSTAINABILITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

The present paper advocates that instead of placing courses under various names of value education, human rights, democracy, etc., into curricula; integration of ethical intelligence would create a dynamic change in the behavior of 21st century learners. This inclusion will enable to achieve SDG 4 in Higher Education institutions. More committed and skilled teachers will motivate the students to develop empathy love, sharing, respect, for the teachers and become respectful citizens of the society. The National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) has developed the National Curriculum Framework (NCF) 2005, which emphasizes on ethical development, inculcating the values, attitudes and skills required for living in harmony with oneself and others. NCERT has developed curriculum, syllabi, text-books and other curriculum materials for elementary and secondary stages, integrating different aspects of value education and at the same time providing adequate space to study the contents of different subjects. A revitalization of curriculum which will include ethical intelligence, traditional Indian value and all basic human and constitutional values as envisaged by National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The new generation thrives to achieve its best in all aspects of life due to which they like to be successful without failure. Any discontent leads to aggression and they are not ready to face the challenges. Lack of ethical intelligence in youth causes them to face the undesirable consequences in their life. Besides Linguistic and Mathematical intelligence, ethical intelligence is the need of 21st century learners. In the view of bringing an overall change in the attitude of present generation in learning English Language, the present paper highlights the importance of Ethical intelligence for SDG 4 in Education.

Keywords: *Ethical Intelligence, Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG) In Education, NEP 2020.*

Introduction

The New Education Policy announced by government of India (NEP 2020) was a welcoming change and great news amidst all the negative issues surrounding the world due to the challenges posed by Covid 19 pandemic. NEP 2020 announcement of the policy was purely unexpected by many. The New Education Policy was an attempt to bring out the rejuvenation of the education system to bring out quality of teaching. Though the education policy has impacted school and college education equally, this paper mainly focuses on NEP 2020 and its impact for sustainability in Higher Education institutions. The National Education Policy 2020, which was approved by Union Cabinet of India on 29th July 2020 outlines the vision of India's new education system. The New Policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. In both rural and urban India, the program provides a comprehensive framework for education. This includes elementary education to Higher Education as well as vocational training. The NEP highlighted that the cultural ethos and the value system is dependent on education at all levels which is the backbone of any society and policy. The main purpose of this paper is to convey what all the things needs to be adopted in our current education system from ancient and medieval times and also some new trends associated with it for achieving SDG 4 in Education.

Ethics in Ancient Times

In ancient times, the education was mostly imparted in ashrams, gurukul, temple, houses, sometimes pujaris of temple used to teach students. The ancient education focused on imparting ethics like humility, truthfulness, discipline, self-reliance and respecting all creation to the students. The parishads or academics were the place of higher learning and education where students learn through discussion and debates, goshti or conference. These were the places where the states used to invite scholars from every institute to meet and exchange their views. The ancient system of education focused on the all-round development of students. The system placed more emphasis on practical knowledge rather than theoretical knowledge. There was no pressure laid on student related to studies so that they can learn effectively.

Ethics in Medieval times

Bhagavat Gita, the famous dialogue between Krishna and Arjuna in the middle of the Kurukshetra battle, popularly considered as a sacred text of moral code, is a liberating text. As even Arjuna surrenders to Krishna, pleading for removal of his confusion and inability to decide. In this crucial moment, Krishna begins by instructing on the imperishable nature of self. Self-knowledge is presented as a means to salvation. The prerequisite for self-enquiry is shown as an ethical life that is mentioned as Karma Yoga. The respect of Lord

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Arjun for his guru's was reflected in the epic "Mahabharata" Even in the battlefield he was forced to think deeply for education and values imparted by his GURUS. Lord Krishna guided Lord Arjuna, he counsels Arjuna by preaching him the ideas of birth, eternal soul, divinity, self-knowledge, jyana yoga, karma yoga. The second chapter of Bhagavat Gita is a summarized text of entire scripture. To quote, Lord Krishna says,

***You have the right to work, But
never to the fruit of work.***

***You should never engage in action for the sake of reward, nor should
you long for inaction.***

***The wise man lets go off all results
Whether good or bad and is focused On
the action alone***

In the literature of medieval India, we find the basis of morality as the striking chord for inner growth and universal peace. There was an emphasis on observance of the samanya dharma irrespective of any societal classification and a reiteration of visesa dharma (specific duties) in which the individual interprets universal laws and applies them to their lives in the apparent reality with regards to everything: lifestyle, diet, money, work, family, sex, marriage, how one relates to people and environment one lives in, technology, etc.

Ethics through Aesthetics

The contribution of aesthetics in augmenting the moral condition of the society is indeed remarkable. The creative expression of any art form reflects the many facets including the moral condition of a said society in a particular time and place. In the Indian tradition of ethical development, aesthetics has played a vital role which can be traced to earliest available so far, the Natyashastra of Bharata. Bharata categorized as the "Father of Indian Dramaturgy" was himself a moralist who expounds in his Natyashastra that the very "Natyashastra" emerged in order to reestablish the diminishing value system. People were overpowered by anger, jealousy, etc. and have forgotten their own duty to perform. Natyashastra was meant to reach out to all sections of the society and present various dharma structure with audio-visual effect. The varied literature reveals the changing value structure thereby indicating the changing life standard. This inevitable and assimilation of their values helps the youth of present generation to lead a life of moral code and conduct. The diminishing ethical values are enlightened with the audio-visual presentation.

Significance of the Study

The present study emphasizes on the enrichment of ethical values amongst the 21st century learners to imbibe the zeal, equity and love for our country India. The most important aims of education for teaching and Teacher Education should be social responsibility, social change and social justice. The present paper highlights the impact of Reading comprehension on students for inculcating moral values and achieving the SDG 4 in Education.

Research Objective

- 1) To find out the impact of Reading comprehension in teaching English Language to B.Ed. students.
- 2) To find out the impact of ethical values on male and female B.Ed. students for achieving the SDG 4 in Education.

Research Hypothesis

Following hypothesis was framed for the study:

- 1) There is no significant effect of Reading comprehension in teaching a second language to B.Ed. students.
- 2) There is no significant effect of ethical values on male and female B.Ed. students for achieving the SDG 4 in Education.

Methodology

Research Design: The researcher has gone through existing literature on English language and benefits of Reading comprehension in Teacher Education institutions. The researcher used Reading techniques for teaching and learning in B.Ed. college. Parallel group experimental method was adopted in the study. The true experimental design employs randomization to provide for control of the equivalence of groups and exposure to treatments. The pre - test post - test Equivalent Groups Design was adopted for the study. Sample: The study was confined to 60 pre-service teachers of Nirmala College of Education, Ujjain. 30 pre-service teachers were considered as controlled group and another 30 pre-service teachers were considered as a tool for study. The control group was not allowed to get any exposure on the subject matter than the traditional

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classroom teaching but the experimental group of pre-service teachers were given treatment by using Reading techniques in teaching English language for a week. Tools: Tryst With Destiny a chapter in English Foundation was selected for Reading comprehension. Where the Mind is without Fear, this poem was selected to create the zeal for equity, and love for our country, India. A self-made achievement test was constructed by the researcher for the study which consisted of worksheets including objective type questions for the study. Analysis Technique: The data was collected and analysed keeping the objectives in view and the design of the study. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were worked out to describe the nature of data. In order to find out the perceived influence of Reading comprehension in teaching and learning, t-test was employed. The controlled group was taught by the traditional method for a week. But the experimental group was taught using Reading comprehension for a week. Thus, the effectiveness of Reading techniques was determined for SDG 4 in Teacher Education.

Data Analysis

Table. 1 Pre - test score of control and experimental groups of pre-service teachers in teaching
Comparison of the difference between the means of pre - test scores of experimental and control groups of pre-service teachers in teaching

Groups	N	df	Mean	SD	Critical Ratio
Control	30	29	9.2	1.55	1.05
Experimental	30		9.6	1.51	

Post - test score of control and experimental groups of pre-service teachers in teaching

Table. 2 Comparison of the difference between the means of post test scores of experimental and control groups of pre-service teachers in teaching

Groups	N	Df	Mean	SD	Critical Ratio
Control	30	29	10.56	1.68	5.75**
Experimental	30		12.86	1.53	

Graph 2

Results and Interpretation

In pre-test, the obtained value of critical ratio for the experimental and control group is 1.05. The table values at .01 level and at .05 level are 1.69 and 2.46 respectively. The obtained value is less than the table values and is not significant at .05 level, (C.R.= 1.05, df =29). From this it is clear that the pre-service teachers of the two groups do not differ significantly in their initial achievement in teaching before experiment. In post-test, the obtained value of critical ratio for the experimental and control groups is 5.75. The obtained value is greater than the table values and is significant at .05 level and .01 level, (C.R.= 5.75, df =29). From this it is clear that the pre-service teachers of the experimental group had shown better performance in teaching. Reading comprehension has proved useful in teaching and learning. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

Findings

The findings of the study revealed that integrating and practicing moral intelligence activities into each and every lesson of any subject matter will develop co-operation and mutual understanding in peer group. The inclusion of intelligence and morality in Teacher Education programs will create a dynamic change in the behavior of teachers and will prepare more skilled and committed teachers for 21st century learners. Logical and verbal intelligence alone cannot help to develop compassion and humanity in the 21st century learners. The Teacher education programs should organize seminars, workshops and symposium to emphasize on knowledge, skills, values, attitude and strategies that will enable them to infuse these amongst the 21st century learners.

Recommendations

The New Education Policy 2020 focused on Millennium Development Goals MDG-3 to implement quality teaching to be inculcated in Teacher Education program. To achieve this vision a varied set of skills and competencies is needed that would allow learners to act as change agents who can achieve positive impact on their surroundings by developing empathy and anticipating the consequences of their actions. To cope with the constantly changing landscape, the educational systems should empower learners with skills and competence to face the challenges of society. To achieve success, NEP 2020 aims to develop all capacities of human-beings intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional and moral in an integrated manner. The NEP long term plan, as per the policy is to do away with the current system of colleges affiliated to universities and focus on ethical intelligence for the new generation.

Conclusion

Our education system needs to learn from ancient and medieval education system regarding the implantations of practical knowledge, ethical values, student-teacher relations, ways of life student lived in that age, the contribution of kings towards education. The National Education Policy 2020 has stipulated that attaining foundational literacy and numeracy for all students must become an immediate national mission. Towards this, the Department of School Education & Literacy has launched a National Mission called National Initiative for Proficiency in Reading with Understanding and Numeracy (NIPUN Bharat), for ensuring that every child in the country necessarily attains foundational literacy and numeracy by the Grade 3,

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by 2026-27. All effort for its implementation has been structured in the NEP 2020 for achieving a holistic development of Teacher education and elementary as well as Higher Education institutions. The need for Sustainable Development 4 encourages quality education as its goal for the future generation.

References

- [1] Altan Mustafa Zulfuk (2017). Moral Intelligence for More Diverse and Democratic World. European Journal of Education Studies. 3 (3). ISSN:2015-1111. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.290612.
- [2] Kumar Sunil (2020). Value Based Education now an integral part of New Education Policy 2020. Bharat, India. TOI.
- [3] Biswas A. K. (2016). Development of Education in India during the Medieval Period: A Historical Approach. International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR) 3(2)260-266. ISSN: 2349-5138.
- [4] Ghonge Mangesh M., Bag Rohit and Singh Aniket (2020). Indian Education: Ancient, Medieval and Modern. Education at the intersection of Globalization and Technology. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.93420.

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A ROLE ON CLASSROOM LEARNING PRODUCTIVITY OF THE STUDENTS

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Abstract

For students, productivity refers to their efforts and aptitude to perform efficiently in their studies. This involves how well they achieve their time, their ability to prioritize, and their overall input into attaining academic success. Whether a student, college, or graduate student, it was significant to look out for ways to be productive in education by focused on the things that will help meet the goals. This is one of the ways we can move to the next stage in life. Productivity for students is measured by only measuring their academic performance. It is the cumulative outcome of hard work in assignments, school projects and studying for examinations. Excelling in education can be qualified to many features aside from a student's personal efforts and circumstances. The quality of learning is an important influence. It's like garbage in, garbage out; the output depends on the effort. If an educational institution aims only to produce excellent students. In that case, they must participate in high-quality learning and other things that will lead to good academic presentation. This will, in turn, give students all the important tools needed to make good grades.

Keywords: *Classroom, Learning, Environment, Students, Materials*

Introduction

Education's productivity is important at many levels. At one level it is about the understanding of different potential and personal success and attaining that in an appropriate length of time. The learning productivity approach to higher education attempts to gain productivity, not so much by reducing inputs but by attractive higher education's major output: student learning. In the learning productivity perspective, the principal problem is in teaching and learning inefficiencies such as excessive non learning time, employed learning, extreme course-taking, and deprived learning.

Classroom Learning Productivity

For students, productivity refers to their efforts and ability to perform proficiently in their studies. This involves how well they achieve their time, their ability to prioritize, and their overall input into attaining academic achievement. The literature on productivity in education is extensive. The object of this effort is to find a construction function a mathematical appearance of the relationship between efforts and outputs in education.

Increase The Productivity In Education

The efforts you make and the strategy we use will help increase your productivity in education. It is not always about how hard work, but how well. As a student, follow these tips to increase your academic productivity.

Set Up the Short-Term Academic Goal

Prior to the start of each academic session, write down the aim in order to boost productivity. If the aim is to achieve a particular grade, this must be stated in the plan. For example, if you need to earn four as in your classes to raise your GPA, mention it in the strategy. These short-term objectives will provide a clear path to your long-term objectives. Additionally, it illustrates the present work required to reach their goal CGPA. Our awareness of the goals we must achieve each academic year will keep us on our toes.

Draft a Study Timetable

Creating a study timetable and sticking to it will increase your productivity levels. Now that you have a clear-cut plan, we need to create a strategy and a schedule that will provide an appropriate guide for it to be accomplished. To create a healthy balance between life and academics, we need to factor in all the extracurricular activities and social commitment while drafting the timetable. Ensure that it does not clash with the other activities. Also, include how much time are going to spend studying. Space it out and include enough time for rest. If we are experiencing some challenges with retaining information, take an online course that will help improve and maximize memory.

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Eliminate all Distractions

Eliminating all distractions is one way of staying productive in the study time. Before start studying, ensure do so in a quiet environment where will not be tempted to do anything besides studying. For instance, if we have the urge to switch on the TV while studying, choose a room without a TV. We can also eliminate distractions by optimizing our study station. Organize study desk; it will help you focus better.

Reduce Screen Time

Reduce screen time by switching or silencing phone when studying. Phone can be your best friend and worst rival, especially when it is standing between academic goal. Switching off phone will help focus better. If you study with phone, we may begin to wonder how to manage without it. But not to worry, some apps will help block other apps, particularly social media apps, during the study period. Social media can be addictive, and these apps can help become more creative.

Practice Compartmentalization During the Study

Dividing the study materials into sections will increase productivity levels. A large number of study materials can be overwhelming, and it can discourage you from studying. To overcome this, divide the study material into sections and schedule a specific time to review each section of the material. The fast reader, start practicing speed reading by incorporating speed reading techniques such as skimming, scanning, the track-and-pace method, and chunking when reading the materials. We can also try out a speed reading tool. It will help increase reading pace.

Technology and Productivity in the Classroom

A systematic approach to the processes and resources of teaching, educational technology or EdTech, empowers classrooms to improve students' performance. Technology provides individualized tutoring and practice to students one-on-one, with the computer acting as a facilitator. It identifies the needs of individuals, adapts technology to classroom instruction, and tracks the academic progress of students. The reason for technology in the classroom is that it makes learning and teaching data-driven. It requires teachers to reveal the needs of students accurately so that they can determine and apply the right technology to the curriculum and track the learning outcomes. Educational technology is a relatively new field in the education area, and not all teachers are ready to start implementing such technologically-driven plans. Technology has made education easily accessible and flexible.

Ways to Increase Classroom Productivity

It's quite hard to measure productivity in education. Educators might not have full control over all situations

Maximize Learning Time

- 1) One reason for low classroom productivity is when there is too much idle period between lessons and classroom activities.
- 2) This could be because of the lack of preparation from the teacher.
- 3) We should do the planning of school tasks days before. This will allow you to prepare the materials needed. Likewise, it's also crucial to set explicit instructions so you and the students will see eye to eye.
- 4) Writing a lesson plan from scratch doesn't have to be daunting. If writing is too colossal of a task, hiring help services could be a good bet.

Boost Student Collaboration

- 1) Group activities can motivate those students who don't enjoy speaking in large classes.
- 2) Dividing them into small groups can encourage team independence.
- 3) It will also allow the students to express their ideas and opinions, or share their knowledge.
- 4) Letting students work in groups can also create healthy competition between other groups.

Here are a Few Ways We Can Make Group Collaboration Fun

- 1) **Create challenging activities.** Making the group work needs group effort. More often than not, straightforward tasks will only allow those high achievers to work on them alone. But challenging activities will encourage others' insights.
- 2) **Keep groups to five students.** Keeping kids busy in smaller groups will discourage students

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to let others do all the work. You may also ask them to assign roles to the members of a group, so everyone knows what to bring to the table.

- 3) **Encourage debates within groups.** Debates are excellent for stirring student knowledge. But make sure you set rules on debate structure. Push team members to communicate, disagree, and even step up to decision-making processes. Check out these tips to conduct a class debate.
- 4) **Provide timely guidance.** Challenging activities can put pressure on students. It's your role as an educator to be always ready to help whenever they need it. Provide timely guidance, but remind yourself to not spoon-feed.

Establish the Need to Participate

- 1) Letting students take part can also allow them to get their ideas across. To some, this could be a walk in the park. Yet, students who fear public speaking could see this as an intimidating method.
- 2) They say that the environment influences how a student performs. That said, make sure you arrange the classroom in a way that encourages participation.
- 3) Next is to establish that participation is one basis for student grades.
- 4) Last, make sure that you value everyone's responses. Memorizing student names will allow you to engage with each one of them.
- 5) Although there are those who regularly volunteer for answers, don't disregard them. Let them know you appreciate them, but would like to hear others speak.

Encourage More Downtime

- 1) A 2016 study says elementary students focus more on 10-minute than 30-minute lessons. The study found young students often struggle to stay focused for long periods. However, shorter lessons of around ten minutes each kept student attention high.
- 2) Research shows when we take breaks, our brains work hard to make sense of our experiences by processing and consolidating the memories.
- 3) Letting students take more classroom breaks contributes to higher levels of classroom productivity. Taking breaks can also reduce stress in the classroom and boost brain functionality.
- 4) But breaks don't have to be a period where students do absolutely nothing. We could ask them to take a few stretching exercises or play quick games to enhance their mood.

Role on Classroom Learning Productivity

Productivity means the quality/quantity of output per the number of inputs used. The best way to measure a student's performance or productivity is a student's success. Some examples of success are degrees, employment, high wages, character, or academic achievement. Also, teachers can gauge a student's interest by checking the following signs:

- 1) If students are listening with attention
- 2) When they take part in class activities
- 3) When they engage with other students
- 4) If students are curious and ask questions
- 5) If they are naturally happy sitting through the class

Conclusion

Productivity for students involves the effort a student puts into their academics. This can be measured by evaluating how well they perform in their grades. Students can increase their productivity by drawing up a short-term goal, drafting a study timetable, eliminating all distractions, partaking in a study group, getting enough sleep, reducing screen time, practicing compartmentalization, and avoiding delay. Improvement our productivity and excel in your studies by signing up for this personal productivity course. It will prepare you with all the materials we need to be a productive student.

References

- [1] Cohen, E. G. (1994). Restructuring the classroom: Conditions for productive small groups. *Review of educational research*, 64(1), 1-35.
- [2] Hamermesh, D. S., & Parker, A. (2005). Beauty in the classroom: Instructors' pulchritude and putative pedagogical productivity. *Economics of Education Review*, 24(4), 369-376.

A STUDY ON THE AWARENESS LEVEL ON CYBER SECURITY AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The penetration and influence of technology in our daily life is increasing day by day. Now a days the invasion and incorporation of technology in our lives is an inevitable one. Technology become a necessity rather than a facility. In the other side, technology also offers so many threats and challenges to us. Without proper awareness one may confront serious dangers. With each passing day cyber threats and cyber crimes have been increasing like anything. As far as the school students are concerned there are a number of students who commit suicide because of being the victims of cyber crimes. With the intention of protecting information assets, attitudes and behaviour of users should be combined with knowledge. Normative survey method is adopted for the present study. The sample for the present study consist of 75 higher secondary school students studying in Plus two under state syllabus. The sample were selected from KV Sanskrit Higher Secondary School, Muthukulam., Alappuzha district, Kerala. The investigator prepared a Questionnaire for the present study. The investigator also use an expert validation schedule to validate the tool. The major statistical techniques used for the analysis and interpretation of the data are Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, T-test, Percentage Analysis. From the analysis of the data, it is clear that majority of students doesn't have proper awareness on cyber Security. Through percentage analysis, responses of item numbers 7, 8, 12, 20, 24 and 25 shows the strong level of ignorance of the students regarding cyber security standards. It is evident that majority of the students overuse internet facilities and also majority students don't care much about their safety while using internet. They do chat with unknown people and use public networks to connect with their personal gadgets. By considering the t value it is evident that there is no significant difference in the level of awareness on Cyber security among higher secondary school students with respect to gender. From the study it can be concluded that the level of awareness on cyber security among higher secondary students is low. Most of the students are not giving any concern regarding their privacy and cyber security. So the authorities should give more emphasis for making awareness on cyber crimes and threats around us.

The penetration and influence of technology in our daily life is increasing day by day. Now a days the invasion and incorporation of technology in our lives is an inevitable one. Technology become a necessity rather than a facility. In the other side, technology also offers so many threats and challenges to us. There are 800 million mobile phone users and 140 million web users in India according to latest statistics. Face book says, around 85 million people uses facebook through smartphones in India. From these statistics, it is evident that besides the age, most of the populations use the technology especially smart phone based technology as apart and parcel of their life. but unfortunately most of them doesn't have any basic idea on the threats and challenges behind these technology. They are not familiar with maintaining cyber security standards. That is why the number of cyber crimes rises in a huge rate. Cyber crimes are the crimes committed with the help of technology. It is broadly a=classified into technological device as a weapon well as target. The objective of the cyber criminals may differ, but mode of operandi lies with in the above classification. It may be against person, against property or against country. Aim may be financial theft, data theft, denial of service attack, stalking, hacking etc. Cybercrimes are defined as the "offences that are committed against individuals or groups of individuals with a criminal motive to intentionally harm the reputation of the victim or cause physical or mental harm, or loss, to the victim directly or indirectly, using modern telecommunication networks such as the Internet (networks including but not limited to chat rooms, emails, notice boards and groups) and mobile phones (Bluetooth/SMS/MMS)". Cyber security, focuses on protecting computers, networks, programs and data from unintended or unauthorized access, change or destruction. Governments, military, corporations, financial institutions, hospitals and other businesses collect, process and store a great deal of confidential information on computers and transmit that data across networks to other computers. With the growing volume and sophistication of cyber attacks, ongoing attention is required to protect sensitive and personal information, as well as safeguard national security.

Need and Significance of the Study

Cyber security standards are of paramount significant in the day today life of an individual who lives in the digital era. Without proper awareness one may confront serious dangers. With each passing day cyber threats and cyber crimes have been increasing like anything. As far as the school students are concerned there are a number of students who commit suicide because of being the victims of cyber crimes. With the intention of protecting information assets, attitudes and behaviour of users should be combined with knowledge. It

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implies that the users understand the threats that are facing them and they can apply appropriate measures to prevent such threats. Exposure to something can have both positive and negative impacts. Therefore a deep contemplation as well as research is inevitable in this topic to find out whether online learning has any influence in improving the cyber security standards in students of higher secondary level.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the awareness level on Cyber Security among higher secondary school students
- 2) To find out the awareness level on Cyber Security among higher secondary school students with respect to gender

Hypotheses

- 1) The awareness level on Cyber Security among higher secondary school Students are low
- 2) There exist significant difference in the awareness level on Cyber Security among higher secondary school students with respect to gender

Methodology

The study conducted was survey in nature. The investigator prepared a questionnaire consists of 50 questions. The population of the study was higher Secondary school students. The sample comprised of 60 students studying in Plus two in a recognised higher secondary school under state syllabus Population: Higher secondary school students in Kerala under state syllabus. Sample selected for the study: The sample for the present study consist of 60 higher secondary school students studying in ninth standard. The sample were selected from KV Sanskrit Higher Secondary School , Muthukulam.,Alappuzha district,Kerala. Tools used for the present study: The investigator prepared a Questionnaire for the present study. The investigator also use an expert validation schedule to validate the tool. Statistical techniques used: The major statistical techniques used for the analysis and interpretation of the data are following:

- 1) Calculation of Arithmetic Mean
- 2) Calculation of Standard Deviation
- 3) T- test
- 4) Percentage Analysis

Analysis and Interpretation

Percentage analysis , Mean, standard deviation and t value of the sample are found and their details and findings are given below from the analysis of the data, it is clear that majority of students doesn't have proper awareness on cyber security. Through item analysis, responses of item numbers 7, 8, 12, 20, 24 and 25 shows the strong level of ignorance of the students regarding cyber security standards. It is evident that majority of the students overuse internet facilities and also majority students don't care much about their safety while using internet. They do chat with unknown people and use public networks to connect with their personal gadgets.

Data and result of test of significance of difference between mean awareness scores of sample with respect to gender.

Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation	T Value
Girls	14.73	3.06	1.77
Boys	13.32	2.91	

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By analysing the value it is evident that there is no significant difference in the level of awareness among higher secondary school students with respect to gender.

Scope of the Study

It is hoped that the study will help to understand the awareness level on cyber Security among higher secondary school students. The result of the study will help the school authorities as well as parents to assess the children and to take necessary steps to make the students aware of the cyber world and its security challenges.

Findings of the Study

The awareness level on cyber crime among higher secondary school students is low. There is no significant difference in the awareness level cyber security among higher secondary school students with respect to gender.

Suggestions and Educational Implications

As we know our world is now ruled by technology ,of course it is inevitable in our day to day life. In the realm of education too, internet has its significant role. It became even more reliable during the Covid19 scenario. Owing to the online classes conducted via online students got more opportunities to be online. As the coin has two sides everything has pros and cons. Therefore proper guidance and awareness should be given to students regarding cyber world and cyber security. In schools awareness classes can be conducted to make them understand the cyber crimes and its consequences.

Educational Implications of the Study

Educational implications of the study is that the teacher could understand the awareness level of students regarding cyber security standards. It open teacher's eyes towards the need of guidance and awareness in the topic among students at higher secondary level.

Conclusion

From the study it can be concluded that the awareness level on cyber security among higher secondary students is low. Most of the students are not giving any concern regarding their privacy and cyber security. So the authorities should give more emphasis for making awareness on cyber crimes and threats around us.

References

- [1] Math favors Indians and I am a mathematician: Google chief. NDTV.Retrieved on 20th February 2014 from <http://www.ndtv.com/article/india/mathfavours-india-and-i-m-a-mathematician-google-chief-345403>.
- [2] NDTV (February 8, 2013b). Facebook has 71 million active users in India. NDTV.Retrieved on 25th May 2013 from <http://gadgets.ndtv.com/social-networking/news/facebook-has-71-million-activeusers-in-india-50-million-duplicate-accounts-worldwide-328213>.
- [3] Umarhathab, S., Rao, G. D. R., &Jaishankar, K. (2009). Cyber Crimes in India: A Study of Emerging Patterns of Perpetration and Victimization in Chennai City. *Pakistan Journal of Criminology*, 1(1), 51-66, April 2009.
- [4] Halder, D., &Jaishankar, K. (2010).*Cyber Victimization in India: A Baseline Survey Report*.
- [5] Tirunelveli, India: Centre for Cyber Victim Counselling.
- [6] Abolarinwa, O., Tiamiyu, M., &Eluwa, S. (2015). Computer Ethics and Security Awareness Behavior of Tertiary Institution Students In South-Western, Nigeria. *Engineering Science and Technology: an international journal*, 5, 260-265
- [7] ETCISO May 24, 2020, Cyber crime trends, digital safety amidst COVID-19 pandemic,<https://ciso.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/cyber-crime-trends-digital-safety-amidst-covid-19-pandemic/75934732>

Introduction

Education is an important tool which is very useful in everybody's life. Education is what differentiates us from other living beings on the earth. It empowers humans and gets them ready to face challenges of life efficiently. It ensures the highest levels of academic achievement for all students and it helps students develop a positive self-concept by providing knowledge about various dimensions of teaching. The legal definition of persons with disabilities includes those who have long term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in conjunction with attitudinal and environmental barriers may prevent them from fully and effectively participating in society on an equal basis to other people. Education is important for all children, but even more so for children with disabilities, whose social and economic opportunities may be limited. The special education system has given children with disabilities much greater access to public education, established an infrastructure for educating them, helpful with the earlier identification of disabilities and promoted greater inclusion of the children along side their nondisabled peers. According to the convention on the rights of persons with disabilities (CRPD) inclusive education is essential to realizing the right to education for all without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunities including for persons with disabilities. The Persons with Disabilities Act 1995 gives a significant step in the direction for people with disabilities and their full participation in the nation building. It allows the students to enjoy the education and gain confidence due to individual learning.

Views of Disability

Students with disabilities need extra support they can't get in a general education classroom so need special education settings. Students with disabilities could be disruptive to other students so they should be educated separately. Students with disabilities can be a drain on limited resources in an educational environment.

Common Disabilities

- 1) Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.
- 2) Learning disabilities.
- 3) Mobility disabilities.
- 4) Medical disabilities.
- 5) Psychiatric disabilities.
- 6) Visual impairments.
- 7) Deaf and hard of hearing.

Problem with Learning Disability

- 1) Students with learning and attention issues often experience feelings of failure.
- 2) Lack of acceptance among their peers and high levels of bullying which increase the risk of misbehavior and absenteeism.
- 3) Negative emotions can exacerbate academic struggles and school climate can also be a significant factor.
- 4) Physical inaccessibility.
- 5) Lack of awareness.
- 6) Unavailability of accessible study materials.

Features of programs initiated for disabled children

- 1) The knowledge of diverse needs, disabilities, and giftedness.
- 2) Skills to develop appropriate programs for diverse needs.
- 3) Adoption of a good approach to ideologies and teaching methodologies.
- 4) Ability to teach at the elementary level in multiple settings.
- 5) Integration of different disciplines-medical, paramedical, therapeutic, social sciences,

psychology and human development.

- 6) Development of resource centres in each school-journal, books, project materials, etc.,
- 7) Inculcation of humanism, sensitivity, inquiry, and creativity.
- 8) Raising of critical concerns and issues, and relating them to temporary needs.

Education Law for the Disabled

Children with disabilities shall have the right to free books, scholarships, uniform and other learning material. Special schools for children with disabilities shall be equipped with vocational training facilities. Non formal education shall be promoted for children with disabilities. All the children with special needs must be enrolled in primary schools. After the assessment of their disabilities by a term of a doctor, a psychologist and a special educator in schools the child will be placed in appropriate educational settings. The disability standards cover specific areas of an educational service. i.e., enrolment, participation, curriculum, support services, preventing harassment and victimisation. The right to education is available to all citizens including the disabled. Article 29(2) of the constitution provides that no citizen shall be denied admission into any educational institution by the state. Article (45) of the constitution directs the state to provide free and compulsory education for and disabled children attain the age of 14 years.

Organisations Working for Education of Disabled Children

The Sikshit Yuva Sewa Samiti (SYSS), an NGO in a partnership with the government, participates in the implementation of the integrated education for disabled children and DPEP (district primary education programme) projects. It also strengthens the program through community based intervention initiatives. The projects provide physical infrastructure for schools through trained personnel and ensure accessibility for an enrolment of children with disabilities in community schools. Trained Anganwadi (grassroots) workers play a crucial role in this activity. The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is another initiative towards the education of children with disabilities. The focus on SSA is very essential, as it is currently heralding the biggest educational movement in the country. Discussions here focus on issues of access, it also raises important concerns about the quality of education being delivered. SSA also examines the role of the non-governmental sector in educating children with disabilities. It also reflects briefly on the rate of participation in early childhood education. In keeping with the diversity that underpins the social cultural and economic makeup of India. The Joyful Inclusion Training Program is being conducted by the CBR network, an NGO. It is involved in the education and rehabilitation of children with special needs. Teachers in rural government schools utilize a training pack that includes a curriculum based criterion. Teachers have been trained in the methodology developed in the joyful inclusion package for teaching all children including disabilities. The helping body Sir Shapurji Billimoria Foundation is a teacher development initiative, which provides in service training for ordinary teachers to meet the needs of children with disabilities. Central and state governments have taken a number of initiatives to improve the enrolment, retention and achievement of children with disabilities. The Government of India also provided a comprehensive education scheme for disabled children in compliance with section 30 of the disabilities act 1995 in the year 2004.

Conclusion

In order to meet the challenges and surmount the hurdles that stand in the way of implementing Right to Education Act for disability children, it is needful to concentrate all efforts with full dedication and commitment. Despite the above challenge of inclusive education the progress in this direction has been insignificant. No debate is required in this regard. We believe that Inclusive Education is the only answer for 'Education for all' which includes children with disabilities. Sound social, educational and economic rationales for the provisions of childhood disabilities Education development exist. It impacts positively on the development and educational gains of the disability children. The learning will enable the children to provide effective intervention and will bring us closer to achieving goal of preventing school failure through high quality early childhood care and education.

References

- [1] Neal Halfon and others, "The Changing Landscape of Disability in Childhood", *Future of Children* 22, 1(2020).
- [2] Ahmad, F.K. 2015. Issues in identification and assessment of students with learning disabilities in India. *Transience*, vol. 6, 91-107.
- [3] Islam, Q. F. 2017. A study of the educational provisions and inclusive practices in elementary school of Delhi. Faculty of education, New Delhi.

THE UNIQUENESS OF IDEALISTIC PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURAL DIVERSITIES IN THE MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

In the present research paper, a discussion has been undertaken to define 'Idealistic Philosophy and Cultural Diversities in the Multicultural Education'. Idealism is one the oldest philosophy in the World. It begins with Plato, who has taught his philosophy in the ancient Greek city state of Athens. Idealist believing the spiritual ideas and nonmaterial world. They believed that the universe is spiritual essence or soul. They also believed that the Macrocosm and Microcosm concepts. In this research paper, the qualitative analysis has been carried out through ethnographical studies in the Chenalappatti Rural School, Gandhigram, Dindigul District, Tamilnadu, India. The researchers have used the tools of participant observation techniques and studied the cultural characteristics of idealistic philosophy. 63% of cultural anthropological study revealed that idealistic philosophical adaptations. Remaining more or less 30% have expressed, other philosophical beliefs. Further, about 07% students in the rural school, not believed any kind of philosophical ideas. From this qualitative study of ethnographical observation, idealistic way of students has more dominant in the cultural diversities. The researchers strongly recommended that the content of idealistic philosophical values is essential in the curriculum of multicultural education.

Keywords: *Idealism, Cultural Diversities, Macrocosm, Microcosm and Vedic Philosophy.*

Introduction

Idealism Describes Metaphysical Perspective Nature. It Is Reality And Inseparable From Perception And Understanding. It Is Constructed Very Closely To The Ideas Not Ideals. There Are Two Major Systems, Such As Subjective Idealism And Objective Idealism. Subjective Idealism Proposes Materials Objects Exists Whereas, Objectives Idealism Proposes The Existence Of An Objective Consciousness. George Berkeley Said That The 'Essence Of An Object Is To Be Perceived'. But Immanuel Kant Said That Idealism Is Our Modes Of Representation. It Is Our Essential Features Of The Human Mind. In The Philosophy Of Transcendentalism, Kant Proposes That The Objects Of Experience Of Reality. Idealism Is Philosophically Scepticism Nature Also. Ontologically, Idealism Have The Existence Of Things Depends Upon The Human Mind And Also Rejects The Physicalism And Dualism. It Is Consciousness Of Material World. Indian Philosophers Said That The World Of Experience Grounded In The Mind's Perception Of The Physical Body. Buddhism Arguments Mind Only Idealism To A Greater Extent On Phenomenological Analysis Of Personal Experience. 'Belief That Reality Is Made Up Only Of Ideas' Said By Christian Wolff, 1747. Macrocosm Refers To The Universal Ideas Or Related To The Creator Or God Oriented Philosophy, Whereas Microcosm Study The Self-Mind Or Personal Mind Of The Particular Individual. In Our Vedic Philosophical Expression, Brahman And Atman Explained By Our Sages. Brahman Means The Entire Universe Is Created By The God Within The Brahman Atman Is Present. It Means Individual Or Self Is Vital Role. Hence, In Indian Context Of Idealistic Philosophy Is Equal To Macrocosm And Microcosm Subject. It Is Pure Form Of Priori Knowledge. Gandhi's Philosophy Also Emphases The Same Forms Of Ideas. If Priori Is Penetrated In Particular Culture, It Makes Conceptualized. They Followed The Logical Ideas In Their Life-Span Continuously.

Method

In this ethnographical study, participant observation techniques and some guiding questions used for data collection (Table:1). Simple statistical and percentile procedures used for data analysis.

Table: 1 show that Guiding Philosophical Questions Used for Formal Interview

S.No.	Questions
1.	Do you feel that idealism giving satisfaction for perfection?
2.	Do you participate any other philosophical procedures in your daily activities?
3.	Have you had any past experience or no philosophical beliefs?

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Results

The study was observed in the Chenalappatti Rural School through participant observation techniques. And also standardized guiding questions have been used for interview. The collected data were kept confidentially for further analysis.

Table: 2 show that Philosophical Ideas and Beliefs of Chenlappatti Rural School, Gandhigram.

S.No.	Philosophical Ideas and Beliefs	Percentage
1.	Idealistic philosophical views	63%
2.	Other philosophical views	30%
3.	No philosophical beliefs	07%

Discussion and Conclusion

Culture means a way of life or a cherished world view of a group in the society. E.B. Tylor defined, the culture in its ethnographical sense, it is complex whole, which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of the society. There are several reasons multicultural education is a necessary in the current situation. Multicultural education has proved to be the single pervasive social phenomenon of the 21st century. It is essential for academic excellence, equity and existence of multi-ethnic society, the existence of an inter-dependent world and for the promotion of democratic values. In this research study, idealistic philosophy and cultural diversities is predominant role in the particular social groups were observed (Table: 2). This cultural pattern set up is essential for educators, should be aware and promote the such cultural background of the students for positivity using the cultural diversities in the education processes.

References

- [1] Banerjee, A.C., & Sita Ram Sharma. (1999). Sociological and Philosophical Issues in Education. Book Enclave, Jaipur, India. pp. 157-158.
- [2] Basham, A.L., (2004). The Wonder That Was India. PICADOR, London. pp.234-347.
- [3] Brooke Noel Moore & Kenneth Broder., (2011). Philosophy-The Power of Ideas. Tata McGraw Hill Education (P) Ltd. New Delhi. pp. 38-45.
- [4] Chandra. S.S., & Rajendra K. Sharma., (2007). Philosophy of Education. Atlantic Publishers & Distributors (P) Ltd., New Delhi. pp. 41-60.
- [5] Jagannath Mohanty., (2011). Dynamics of Educational Thoughts and Practices. Shipra Publications, New Delhi. pp. 110-123.
- [6] Jagdish Chand., (2010). Philosophical Foundation of Education. Ansh Publishing House, New Delhi -2. pp. 69-79.
- [7] Kalpana, Rajaram., & et.al., (2010). Facets of Indian Culture. Spectrum Books (P) Ltd., New Delhi. pp. 04-15.
- [8] Seetharamu, A.S., (2004). Philosophies of Education. Ashish Publishing House, New Delhi-26. pp. 45-58.
- [9] Zeinrich Zimmer., (2021). Philosophies of India. Bollingen Series XXVI, Princeton and Oxford, London. pp. 74.83.

OUTCOME BASED CURRICULUM

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Abstract

A good teacher preaches; a better teacher teaches, the best teacher demonstrates. The strata in the Educational process, i.e. mainly in teaching learning activity, objectives are important to establish in a pedagogical interchange so that teachers and students alike understand the purpose of that interchange. This metamorphosis helps to clarify the objectives for themselves and for students. A teacher, before teaching a particular content should question oneself “Why am I teaching this? What should my students understand? Will they be able to achieve?” in other words, what will be the outcome of this particular session? If the teacher is able to get the desired objectives so set, and the students learning outcome is aligned with the set objectives; then the Teaching –Learning Process is complete. This is the basis for any Educational Transaction to be complete. This framework was elaborated by Bloom and his collaborators consisted of six major categories. Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis and Evaluation. While each category contained sub categories, all lying on a continuum from simple to complex, concrete to abstract, known to unknown and so on. In any real life situations for any task to be complete, what we plan should be the result of what we wanted to accomplish. This is the paramount factor in the field of Education and hence the elaborate discussion on “Outcome Based Curriculum” is significant in the technology driven era to meet out the needs of the employability skills of the learners.

Foreword

Education is a human right for everyone in the world, regardless of gender, race, colour and socio economic status. It is a powerful engine of development and one of the most effective tools for reducing poverty, improving health, gender equality, peace and stability in human life. For individuals education promotes employment, income and self reliance, thus enhancing qualifications and life skills. Education is the social institution through which society provides its members with the skills, knowledge norms and values to become good and productive members of the society. Today’s children are preparing for a better tomorrow. This growth corresponds to the future of our country, which is reflected in the quality of the current education system. Schools and educational agencies should strike at the spark of the Learner’s needs and give them a rich Learning Experience. Education aims to encourage the development of healthy thought process and the creation of our cognitive abilities. For this, the curriculum which is imparted through the medium of education should be so designed in such a way that it aims to have the desirable outcomes tangible and futuristic.

Curriculum Development

Curriculum Development is a process of improving the curriculum. A Commonly used approach consists of analysis, selecting appropriate teaching/learning and appropriate assessment methods. Outcome Based Curriculum is a package of all such activities that are planned to facilitate the teaching-learning process, from known to unknown, simple to complex, concrete to abstract etc. To enable the process to be able to get the desirable outcomes, tangible and measurable, leading towards enhanced and lifelong learning experience. For this the Curriculum may include along with the content, individual and group activities, field visits, art and craft expositions, seminars, group discussions, quiz programs, creating models, assignments, educational trips, interviews and the list is endless. The design of such a curriculum is the domain of the “Teacher” and the wholehearted partnership of the Teachers and Students plays an important role for the “Outcome Based Curriculum”. Every now and then as the curriculum opens doors to new knowledge and capabilities, a teacher has to question “Why am I teaching?”, “What will the students do after exploring?” Same as the case with the students. This helps in the integration of concepts, theories and techniques. It is a strategic and planned approach to imparting education. It is a comprehensive approach to organize and operate for the market needs and future employment trends.

Outcome Based Curriculum

Education is a strong pillar of stability for a society in general, more so for a quality standard life in particular for any individual. Education based on defined outcomes has absolutely no meaning, if it is not equipped with a structured “Outcome Based Curriculum”. Any set of curriculum is a “set of all those activities, content and skills that are planned during the Teaching- Learning process facilitating the result of such experiences during and at the end of any such program, course and sessions, leading towards extended

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learning outcomes. “What do we want our students to do “—Is the pragmatic approach in this “ Outcome Based Curriculum”. Any such curriculum is a well designed “template”, teaching through knowledge for capabilities. Blooms Taxonomy of Education clearly states how interesting and challenging a curriculum could be.

Why Outcome Based Curriculum

All students can learn and succeed but not all in the same way and at the same time. We need to nurture and develop their learning skills through “ Outcome Based curriculum “. Schools and teachers control this condition. What level of performance should they demonstrate to be able to excel in their perspective and their chosen career and path. “Outcome Based Curriculum” emphasizes setting clear standards for observable and measurable outcomes. It is a students’ centric instructional model. Focuses on measuring performance at all levels i.e. Knowledge, skill and attitude upon completion of a program. This “ Outcome Based Curriculum” is the need of the hour. The Learners have to prove themselves in this competitive world, and a challenging environment. It is an accreditation to ensure quality. National Knowledge Commission insists on “Outcome Based Learning” pointing out

- 1) Curriculum Revision
- 2) Enhancing Reliance on Internal Assessment
- 3) Encouraging Research
- 4) Reforming Governance of Institutions.

Outcome Based Curriculum Aims at Four Important Areas of Insightfulness

- 1) Intended Learning Outcomes
- 2) Alignment
- 3) Outcomes assessment using data on students’ achievements of learning outcomes.
- 4) Continuous improvement.

Illustration

Reference: XII Std Economics Text Book. First Edition 2020. Second Print 2022. © Maharashtra State Bureau of Text Book Production and Curriculum Research, Pune.

Demand Analysis

Some of the competency statements of this topic are discussed as below;

- 1) Knows the term “Utility”
- 2) Understands how the desire of an Individual determines the “demand” for a product or service
- 3) Explains the feature of ‘Market Demand’
- 4) Analyses the relationship of price and quantity of the Product.
- 5) Draws and tabulates the Demand Schedule
- 6) Applies qualitative skills to apply the demand curve.

Exercises provided after each concept or unit are prepared using different parameters such as observation, co-relation, critical thinking, analytical reasoning etc. Evaluation pattern also is dynamic and structured, testing the learners’ knowledge, understanding, application, synthesis and multiple talents, capabilities and skills. The content is well explained with examples drawing from real life situations so that the terms highlighted in the context are clear and illustrative.

Demand Analysis

It is an economic principle referring to a consumers’ desire to purchase goods and services and willingness to pay a price for a specific good or service.

Consumer	Price
/ \	/
Demand	Desire
\ /	\
Wants	Quantity

Demand curve will move downward from the left to right which expresses the law of demand—as the price of a given commodity increases the quantity demanded decreases, all else being equal.

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X AXIS – Quantity sold In Units. Y Axis – Price in Rupees.

Price is independent variable, and quantity the dependant variable.

Now, understanding this concept, the curriculum designer will emulate the trends in market by way of observation, preparation of graphs (Individual and Group), visit to a nearby market, preparing a questionnaires to analyze and synthesis the concept of Demand Analysis.. By designing the curriculum dynamically each level in the Blooms Taxonomy of objectives of “ Learning Outcomes”. Applied to the topic “Demand Analysis”,

The student should be able to

- 1) Interact with the market trend, processes and participate and understand that the concept has a scientific basis.
- 2) Deal with abstractions.
- 3) Work in groups, learning through each others’ help.
- 4) Collect data and analyse to understand the demand for the products “ tomatoes”, “cars” and correlate with other types of products or services.
- 5) Critically analyse the demand for a product or service during the times of famine, shortage, war etc.
- 6) Analyse, why there is a “Energy Crisis” in parts of Europe.
- 7) Synthesise the concept of Demand with other dependant variables.
- 8) Differentiate between exceptional demand and normal demand.

DEMAND = DESIRE + WILLINGNESS TO PURCHASE + ABILITY TO EXERCISES

Identify the concept,

- 1) A poor person wants to buy a car-----
 - 2) A rich person buys a car-----
- I) Prepare a Monthly Demand Schedule of your family for various commodities. For example vegetables, fruits, medicines, entertainment etc.
- II) Find out
- 1) Prestigious goods
 - 2) Habitual goods -----
 - 3) Branded goods
- III) Choose the best option
- 1) When less units are demanded at high price it shows -----
a) Increase in demand b) Expansion of demand c) Decrease in demand d) None
 - 2) Symbolically, the functional relationship between demand and price can be expressed as
 $D_x = f(P_x)$ b) $D_x = f(P_z)$ c) $D_x = f(y)$ d) $D_x = f(T)$

The above exercise helps in evaluation of the “Object Based Curriculum” in eliciting the desired and measurable outcomes.

Conclusion

Outcome Based Curriculum provides multiple learning opportunities to match different learners’ needs. Most students can achieve high standards if they are given appropriate opportunities. Curriculum begins with Exit Outcome followed by “ Building Blocks” of learning. It is the responsibility of the Educational Diaspora to produce graduates who are ready for market demand at global platform and to meet global level of quality assurance. A lot has been done and lot more needs to be done, which is possible by engaging ourselves in seminars, conferences, symposiums and discussions etc. to formulate the policies and procedures in this context.

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Abstract

The process of teaching learning is as old as human beings on earth. It has been carried out by human beings and even by animals to teach their young ones for successful adjustments in the environment. The process has undergone several changes from non-formal to formal with the help of passage of time. The study of gender and education encompasses gender differences in educational outcomes such as achievement, attainment and experiences within the education system.

Introduction

Gender and education focuses on whether differences in the educational outcomes of males and females were due to biological differences. Biological differences play a relatively small role in educational outcomes while other factors like socialization and differences in expectations of boys and girls may play a large role. Thus the primary and secondary school students examined low peer, teacher and family interactions are related to gender differences while research on higher education examined sex segregation by major and gender differences.

Relationship Between Gender And Education

In terms of impacts, several research suggests that low educational attainment can lead to the entrenchment of unequal power structures as well as discriminatory gender norms and attitudes at individual or household level, may be replicated and perpetuated at community level through unequal practices within schools.

Gendered Causes And Effects Of Low Educational Attainment

There are several gendered barriers that children and young people in developing countries are facing the education stem in order to issues, practices and policies at individual, household, school, community, policy, system level, which are including:

1) Individual and Household Level

Low perceived value of girl's education, gendered traditional practices, early marriage, early pregnancy, lack of parental support for education, death or illness of parents, lack of interest in schools, etc

2) School Level

High cost of schooling, lack of nearby school, school related gender based violence, inadequate facilities for girls and women, unequal learning environments, lack of female teachers.

3) Policy and System Level

Inadequate and weak policies are accessed to school for pregnant girls and young mothers, inadequate or weakly enforced legislation on school related gender based violence, inadequate or weakly enforced legislation on harmful traditional practices.

Remedial Measures for Educational Attainment from Gender

- 1) Engendering the gender balance of power at each level of aggregation.
- 2) Challenging common hold norms and perceptions regarding females and males especially their roles and responsibilities.
- 3) Ending the great harmful traditional practices.
- 4) Strengthening the boosts or the rights of or improving an opportunity for the groups that are disadvantaged based on gender.

Gender in Basic Education

The national gender policy in basic education is the response to the challenges of achieving gender equality in education as expressed in our Nigerian constitution 1999 to access quality education for the rights of every Nigerian child.

Role of Gender and Society in the School Class Room

Gender and education is a broad category where several thematic strands of inquiry emerge:

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socialization in schools, the social experience of schooling, textbooks, books, curriculum, educational attainment, educators, education workers, higher education, cross cultural educational practices.

Gender Equality and Education

- 1) Recent trends analyze gender equality as a relational process through the educational system, norms and values are institutionalized within them.
- 2) To demonstrate this relational process, gender equality is divided into three connected parts of indicating often used to measure effectiveness of each component.
- 3) The three components are Right to education, Rights within education, Rights through education.

Important Aspects of Gender Education

- 1) To understand our rights and fight for them.
- 2) To not differentiate the basis of gender but usage utility and learning.
- 3) To explore social and economic opportunities based on potential.
- 4) To minimize crimes against women.
- 5) To reduce high female infanticide.
- 6) To encourage both boys and girls to enjoy the freedom of speech, movement, marriage, work and social relationships.
- 7) To create a safe environment for girls and boys to express their feelings.
- 8) Gender equality is important for the socio-economic development of our country.

Conclusion

Gender inequality is a nationwide social issue. We are home to some people who still see the birth of a girl child in dismay. Even our orphanages are full of girls children who are mostly abandoned. It is need of our society to bring the desired changes in the mindset and remove the ingrained prejudices that damage India's growth. It is the high time that every child is treated equally and given every opportunity required to grow to his/her full potential.

Reference

- [1] Weaver-Hightower, M. (2003). The "boy turn" in research on gender and education. *Review of educational research*, 73(4), 471-498.
- [2] Grant, C. A., & Sleeter, C. E. (1986). Race, class, and gender in education research: An argument for integrative analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 56(2), 195-211.
- [3] Chisamya, G., DeJaeghere, J., Kendall, N., & Khan, M. A. (2012). Gender and education for all: Progress and problems in achieving gender equity. *International journal of educational development*, 32(6), 743-755.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The process of teaching learning is as old as human beings on earth. It has been carried out by human beings and even by animals to teach their young ones for successful adjustments in the environment. The process has undergone several changes from non- formal to formal with the help of passage of time. Inclusion education differs from integration model of education, tended to be a concern.

Introduction

Inclusion in education refers to all students are being able to access and gain equal opportunities to education and learning. It arose in the context of special education with an individualized education program and is built on the notion that it is more effective for students with special needs to have the mixed experience for them to the successful in social interactions leading to further success in life.

Implementation Of Inclusive Education

The implementation of inclusive education does not prioritize, but still provides for the utilization of special classrooms and special schools for the education of students with disabilities. These models brought into force by educational administrators with the intention of moving away from seclusion models of special education to the fullest extent practical, the idea being to the social benefit of general education students and special students serving as peer models and those less able serving as motivation of general education students to learn empathy.

Moderating Special Needs

Schools are mostly frequent to used the inclusion model for select students with mild to moderate special needs. Fully inclusive schools, are rare, do not separate general education and special education programs; instead, the school is restructured so that all students learn together.

Participation of Students

A premium is placed upon full participation by students with disabilities and upon respect for their social, civil and educational rights. Feeling included is not limited to physical and cognitive disabilities, but also includes the full range of human diversity with respect to ability, language, culture, gender, age and other forms of human differences.

Articulations of Policies and Law

The new anti-discriminatory climate has provided the basis for much change in policy and statute, nationally and internationally. Convention of rights of the child (1989) set out children's rights in respect of freedom from discrimination and in respect of representation of their wishes and views. Convention against Discrimination in education of UNESCO prohibits any discrimination, exclusion or segregation in education. Conventions on the rights of persons with disabilities which calls on all states partiesto ensure an inclusive education system of all levels.

Practices in Classrooms

Students in an inclusive classroom are generally placed with their chronological age mates regardless of whether the students are working above or below the typical academic level for their age. Also, to encourage a sense of belonging, emphasis is placed on the value of friendships. Teachers often nurture a relationship between a students with special needs and a same age student without a special educational need. Another common practice is the assignments of the buddy to accompany a student with special needs at all times. This is used to show students that a diverse group of people make up a community, that no one type of student is better than another, and to remove any barriers to a friendship that may occur if a student is viewed as "helpless".

Techniques Used by the Teachers

- 1) Using games designed to build community.
- 2) Involving students in solving problems.
- 3) Openly dealing with individual differ by discussion.
- 4) Utilizing physical therapy equipment (i.e.) standing frames, so students who typically use

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- wheelchairs can stand when other students are standing and more actively participate in activities.
- 5) Focusing on the strength of students with special needs.
 - 6) Create classroom checklists.
 - 7) Take breaks when necessary.
 - 8) Help establish short term goals.
 - 9) Set ground rules and stick with them.

Conclusion

“Full inclusion”- brings idea of all the children, including those with severe disabilities, should learn in a regular classroom has also taken root in many school systems and most notably in the province of new kind. Children with severe disabilities should learn in a regular classroom has taken room in many school systems.

Reference

- [1] Lindsay, G. (2003). Inclusive education: a critical perspective. *British journal of special education*, 30(1), 3-12.
- [2] Stubbs, S. (2008). *Inclusive education. Where there are few resources*. Oslo, The Atlas Alliance Publ.
- [3] Messiou, K. (2017). Research in the field of inclusive education: time for a rethink?. *International journal of inclusive education*, 21(2), 146-159.

DISCOURSE OF GENDER EDUCATION AND EMPOWERMENT WITH REGARDS TO ADICHIE'S NOVELS PURPLE HIBISCUS AND HALF OF THE YELLOW SUN

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Abstract

Gender Education is termed as the study of gender and education encompasses gender differences in educational outcomes such as achievement, attainment, and experiences within the education system. This field also moves beyond the study of how gender influences educational outcomes and incorporates how these differences impact the labor market, family formation, and health outcomes. Early research in gender and education focused on whether differences in the educational outcomes of males and females were due to biological differences. Over time, research began to show that biological differences between genders tend to be smaller than those within gender. Thus, biological differences may play a relatively small role in educational outcomes while other factors like socialization and differences in expectations of boys and girls may play a larger role. Empowerment - Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines empowerment as being confident and also in control of oneself by acquiring available necessities of life such as education, religion, politics, business etc. The declaration of the Seneca Falls Convention in 1848, using the model of the US Declaration of Independence, forthrightly demanded that the rights of women as right-bearing individuals be acknowledged and respected by the society. It was signed by sixty-eight women and thirty-two men. This paper focuses on the importance of gender education and empowerment of women with reference to the women characters in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's novels Purple Hibiscus and Half of the Yellow Sun. The novels Purple Hibiscus and Half of the Yellow Sun emphasize the need for women to be educated and be economically independent. The importance of education and economic independence are highlighted when the role of Eugene's wife, Beatrice, is contrasted with that of Auntie Ifeoma who is a lecturer at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Keywords: *Education, Gender, Empowerment, Adichie, Economic, Women*

Full Paper

Gender Education is termed as the study of gender and education encompasses gender differences in educational outcomes such as achievement, attainment, and experiences within the education system. This field also moves beyond the study of how gender influences educational outcomes and incorporates how these differences impact the labor market, family formation, and health outcomes. Early research in gender and education focused on whether differences in the educational outcomes of males and females were due to biological differences. Over time, research began to show that biological differences between genders tend to be smaller than those within gender. Thus, biological differences may play a relatively small role in educational outcomes while other factors like socialization and differences in expectations of boys and girls may play a larger role. Empowerment - Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines empowerment as being confident and also in control of oneself by acquiring available necessities of life such as education, religion, politics, business etc. The declaration of the Seneca Falls Convention in 1848, using the model of the US Declaration of Independence, forthrightly demanded that the rights of women as right-bearing individuals be acknowledged and respected by the society. It was signed by sixty-eight women and thirty-two men.

According to Wollstonecraft's *A Vindication of the Rights of Woman* (1792) in which she argues that women are not naturally inferior to men, but appear to be only because they lack education. She suggests that both men and women should be treated as rational beings and imagines a social order founded on reason. This wave ended with the ratification of the Twentieth Amendment of the U.S. Constitution, which protected women's right to vote. First- wave feminism was concerned primarily with establishing, as a point of policy, that women are human beings and should not be treated like properties. This paper focuses on the importance of gender education and empowerment of women with reference to the women characters in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's novels Purple Hibiscus and Half of the Yellow Sun. The novels Purple Hibiscus and Half of the Yellow Sun emphasize the need for women to be educated and be economically independent. The importance of education and economic independence are highlighted when the role of Eugene's wife, Beatrice, is contrasted with that of Auntie Ifeoma who is a lecturer at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Chief Ozoibia's two daughters, Olanna and Kainene, highly educated and independent- minded, disdain marriage and choose relationships with men as lovers, refusing marriage in the traditional and ordinary sense because education has made them believe that relationships last longer than marriage. As result of the level of Auntie Ifeoma's education and economic independence, she appreciates the fact that her father is a traditionalist and not an idol worshipper as Eugene thinks. To correct this impression, she asks Kambili to watch her grandfather pray. Grandpa prays thus:

Chineke! I thank you for this new morning! I thank you for the sun that rises. He bent

down to draw another line . . . chineke I have killed no one, I have taken no one's land, I have not committed adultery . . . He leaned over and drew the third line . . . Chineke I have wished others well. I have helped those who have nothing with the little that my hands can spare . . . Chineke! Bless me. Let me find enough to fill my stomach. Bless my Daughter, Ifeoma, give her enough for her family . . . Chineke! Bless my son, Eugene. Let the sun not set on his prosperity. Lift the curse they have put on him (*Purple Hibiscus*,165-166).

Kambili is surprised that he prays for his son, Eugene who maltreats him by not giving him sufficient money and restrains his grandchildren from visiting him. Grandpa prays for his son Eugene "Chineke! Bless my son, Eugene. Let the sun not set on his prosperity. Lift the curse they have put on him" (166). Aunt Ifeoma's level of education enables her to fight injustice at the university. When she is given notice of termination of her employment, she travels to America with her children and secures another employment. "She writes about her two jobs one at a community College and one at a pharmacy or drugstore as they call it . . ." (292). Olanna, on the other hand fights injustice by supporting the Biafran win-the-war agenda through teaching because their Hausa counterparts molested and destroyed so many Igbo people as they have an edge over Biafra. Ifeoma's education does not make her show dislike for the culture of her people, when Igwe visits Eugene, she bows down and greets the Igwe. Aunt Ifeoma greets the Igwe thus with respect, regardless of her level of education as Kambili accounts: "I watched Aunt Ifeoma sink to one knee and say "Igwe" in the raised voice of a respected salute, watched him pat her back (94). Eugene on the other hand reprimands his children for bowing to another human being. "It was an ungodly tradition bowing to an Igwe" (94).

Economic independence is also projected through Mama Joe, the woman who makes Kambili's hair. This is evident in the following extract:

Mama Joe's shed in Ogige market just barely fit the high school . . . women and children worked in the neighbouring sheds, twisting hair, weaving hair, plating with thread . . . the closet ones read MAMA BOMBOY INTERNATIONAL HAIR. The women and children called out to every female who walked past "let us plait your hair". "Let us make you beautiful" .

. . . Mama Joe welcomed me as though she had been plaiting my hair all my life (*Purple Hibiscus*, 231).

Mama Joe uses this medium to add to her family's economy and can take care of herself. She has something to fall back on unlike Beatrice who is totally dependent on her husband. ANA Abia Review notes that in *Half of a Yellow Sun*, Adichie creates women who are no longer there to carry foofoo and soup to men discussing "important matters":

They have been empowered by education so that at Odenigbo's parties, they hold their own among world-class intellectuals like Odenigbo, Dr Patel, Professor Ezeka and Professor Lehman. The two central female characters, Olanna and Kainene have been educated abroad and Lara Adebayo is also educated. The women we encounter share complete equality with their male counterparts. (15).

The narrative voice tells the reader that Olanna once tells Odenigbo "That she did not have that fabled female longing to give birth, and her uneducated mother had called her abnormal until Kainene said she didn't have it either" (*Half of a Yellow Sun*, 104). Olanna refused repeated marriage proposals from Odenigbo, she had argued that: "They were too happy, precariously so, and she wanted to guard that bond; she feared that marriage would flatten it to a prosaic partnership" (52). Kainene also suggested how she will put her degree into use during a dinner with the finance minister in her father's house. She reports, "I, too, will be putting my newly acquired degree to good use. I'm moving to Port-Harcourt to manage Daddy's business there. . . Kainene is not just like a son, she is like two, her father commented" (31). These women were able to perform certain roles in the society and also support themselves financially and otherwise because they are educated and economically independent. The roles they perform also shows bonding as female characters in one way or the other as the next section will portray. The importance of this research is on the examination of the reality of female empowerment and raised consciousness in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun* and how they have been shown in the lives of women in traditional African society with reference to Nigeria according to the setting of the novel. This research portrays the authors sense of women struggle in their marginalized state in a male dominated society and how education provide for these women economic independence and also coming together to share their views in order to promote sisterhood, self-assertiveness and to destroy the shackles of patriarchy. Adichie's works effectively and realistically capture female self-assertiveness, passivity of female characters, the individuality of the female protagonists, economic independence sisterhood, and war as a factor that destroy the family and the nation. Aunt Ifeoma's conduct in *Purple Hibiscus* is worthy of emulation. Although she is a widow without much financial means, she trains her three children to be independent-minded and vocal. She never dehumanizes them when they err. This is why Amaka, her daughter is able to advise her uncle Eugene on his drink: "Uncle Eugene . . . it is a little too sweet. It would be nicer if you reduce the sugar in it (*Purple Hibiscus*, 98). Olanna, on the other hand,

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shows her assertiveness by refusing to be lashed by her parent's wealth and by the minister of finance's (Chief Okonji) affluence. Instead, she prefers to take decisions and implement them without the interference of her parents.

This is contrary to the docile, submissive, passive and shy tendencies shown by Kambili at the early stage of *Purple Hibiscus*, Beatrice (Kambili's mother) and Mrs Ozobia in *Half of a Yellow Sun*. Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun* call for the empowerment of the female folks and freedom of speech in both the family and the nation. The writer sees education as a veritable tool with which these could be achieved. Adichie is of the strong opinion that female empowerment and raised consciousness contribute immensely to social change in several ways. It is because Aunty Ifeoma is educated that she is able to train her three children, reorientate Jaja and Kambili and defend herself when the school authority at the University tries to intimidate her by sending security personnel to her house. As a result of her level of education, she is able to relocate abroad when her appointment is terminated by the university. Education also helped Kainene to take control of her father's business in Port-Harcourt while Olanna took to teaching Sociology at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. There is no doubt that when females are not empowered, they are prone to the whims and caprices of men who may use them as tools to satisfy their male ego. For instance, because Eugene's wife and Mrs. Ozobia are neither educated nor employed their husbands find it to always intimidate them. Beatrice is beaten incessantly by her husband but she consoles herself with the fact that her husband refuses to marry another wife whereas, Mrs. Ozobia accepts every decision made by her husband and he molest her by having a mistress outside their marriage. Aunty Ifeoma, Olanna and Kainene truly affirm that knowledge is not only power but an instrument of change. They use their education to show that when females empower themselves they will easily have access to new and better jobs, leading to economic independence. Therefore, female empowerment and raised consciousness is an indispensable tool for change in the society as they ensure that both male and female members of the society enjoy equal rights and privileges. Women in the rural areas should disregard the believe that women are meant to carry food to their husbands having important discussions. Women should contribute and give their own opinions in matters discussed because their opinions may lead to greater heights. Therefore, a woman must strive to survive with or without the help of a man, if you are not favoured with children or husband, try to be economically independent and from it gain education, be part of public opinion and make useful decisions. Women should by any means liberate themselves from the forced determined roles given to them and propagate for the peaceful co-existence of men and women in regard to equal rights to the sexes. The notion that women are weaker vessels and illiterates should be gotten rid of in order to build a peaceful and healthy society.

Reference

- [1] Adichie. Chimamanda Ngozi. "Purple Hibiscus". London: Harper Perennial Publishers, 2005. Akpome, Aghogho. "Focalisation And Polyvocality in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Half of a Yellow Sun." *English Studies in Africa* 56.2 (2013): 25.
- [2] Atieh, Majda R., and Ghada Mohammad. "Post-traumatic Responses in the War Narratives of Hanan al-Shaykh's The Story of Zahra and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Half of a Yellow Sun."
- [3] Buchmann, Claudia. Edmunds, Chrisse. "Gender and Education" <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780199756384/obo-97801997563840151.xml#:~:text=The%20study%20of%20gender%20and,experiences%20within%20the%20education%20system>.
- [4] Chukwuemerelam, Cordelia. Female Empowerment And Consciousness Raising In Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Purple Hibiscus And Half Of A Yellow Sun. Veritas University, Abuja, July, 2012.
- [5] Da silva, Tony Simoes. "Embodied Genealogies and Gendered violence in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's writing", *African Identities* 10.4 (2012): 455- 70.
- [6] Rackley, Lauren. "Gender Performance, Trauma, and Orality in Adichie's Half of a Yellow Sun and Purple Hibiscus". Oxford, May 2015.

A STUDY ON UTILIZATION AND AWARENESS OF E- LIBRARY AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS IN YADAGIR DISTRICT

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Abstract

This paper aims to provide the e-library awareness and utilization among the college students in Yadagir district. It also highlights the electronic library facilities available for the students. It lists out the components of e-library and its merits and demerits. Majority of the students are using the library daily and Science and Engineering students using e-resources to prepare for class work.

Keywords: *E-library, Digital Objects, College Students, Yadagir District, Education, Levels, Engineering*

Introduction

Education is the key to all processes of development, especially human development. the catalytic action of education in this complex and dynamic growth process needs to be planned meticulously and executed with great sensitivity. Education is fundamental to the all round development of human potential – material and spiritual. It refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national cohesion, a scientific temper and independence of mind and spirit thus furthering the goal of socialism, secularism and democracy enshrined in our constitution.

E – Resources and Services

The electronic resources are systems in which information is stored electronically and made accessible through electronic systems and computer networks. These resources include OPAC, CD-ROM, Online- database, e-journals, E-books, Internet resources etc. multiple accesses speed, richer in content, reuse, timelines and accessibility anywhere are some of the features of e-resources. IEEE Explore, Elsevier Science Direct, ASCE Journals, ASME Journals, EBSCO, Springer, etc are the examples of some famous e-resources available in India and overseas. These resources are paid resources and only accessible after payment. These resources have only limited access. These are available in so many different packages in different price ranges. In India, these resources are available through INDEST-AICTE consortium and UGC-INFONET consortium on some discounted prices. Electronic resources provide access to information that might be restricted to the users because of geographical location or finances. Electronic resources also provide access to current information as there are often updated frequently.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

In the present study, the investigator analyzed the data using the statistical techniques such as descriptive analysis and different analysis. The descriptive analysis of the data involves computing measures of central tendency as the mean and the measures of a variable like standard deviation.

List of the colleges, which located in Yadagir District (reputed colleges in district)

- 1) S .P College of Arts, Science & Commerce, Shorapur
- 2) Dr Ambedkar First Grade college Rangampet Shorapur
- 3) Jawahar College of Education, Yadagir
- 4) Government First Grade College Shahapur,
- 5) Government First Grade College Shorapur
- 6) Government First Grade College Yadagir
- 7) Government First Grade College, Kembhavi
- 8) Government First Grade College, Hunasagi
- 9) Government First Grade Women's College Yadagir
- 10) Gurukul College of Arts, commerce & Science, Rangampet, shorapur
- 11) Chadrashekhar Degree College, Yadagir
- 12) Subham Degree College, Yadagir
- 13) Nivedita Degree College, Yadagir
- 14) Jawahar Degree College, Yadagir
- 15) Shri Balaji Degree College, Saidapur
- 16) Government First Grade College, Gurumithkal
- 17) Shri S B Deshmukh Degree College, Shahapur
- 18) Prarthana Degree College, shahapur
- 19) Yeshashwini Degree College, shahapur

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- 20) Swamy Vivekanand Degree college, Hunasagi
- 21) Shri Janani Women's Degree College, shorapur
- 22) Lingeri Konappa Degree College, Yadagir
- 23) Veerappa Nisty Engineering College, Shorapur

Level of Significance

The research workers chose several arbitrary standards for the convenience. These arbitrary standards are called 'level of significance'. The most commonly used level of significance is 0.01 and 0.05 level. In the present investigation, the researcher used the 0.05 level of significance to analyze the existence of various hypotheses.

Table 1 The Mean and S.D. of Awareness and Utilization of e – Library Scores of Arts, commerce & Science College Students

S. No.	Variable	Sample	No.	Mean	S.D
1	Gender	Male	30	24.77	2.91
		Female	40	22.00	5.36
2	Locality	Rural	65	21.38	5.17
		Urban	35	23.86	3.19
3	Parents' Education	School	42	21.56	5.37
		College	32	22.30	3.36
		Illiterate	26	24.88	3.49
Entire sample		100	23.02	4.46	100

It is evident from Table 1 that the calculated mean score of the entire sample is 23.02 and the standard deviation value is 4.07. the mean score of the Arts and Science college students is higher than the percentile 75 (20). Hence, it is inferred that college students have a high level of awareness and utilization of e-library. The mean score of sub samples selected by the investigator ranges from 21.38 to 24.88. the mean scores of selected sub samples of the Arts and Science college students are higher than the percentile 75 (20).

Table 2 The Mean and S.D. of Awareness and Utilization of e-Library Scores of Engineering College Students

S. No.	Variable	Sample	No.	Mean	S.D.
1	Gender	Male	97	23.84	3.05
		Female	53	22.58	4.46
2	Locality	Rural	86	23.09	4.53
		Urban	64	23.53	2.67
3	Parent's Education	School	82	23.27	2.85
		College	48	23.47	4.90
		Illiterate	20	23.00	2.60
Entire sample			150	23.13	4.07

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It is evident from Table 2 that the calculated mean score of the entire sample is 23.13 and the standard deviation value is 4.07. The mean score of the Engineering college students is higher than the percentile 75 (20). Hence, it is inferred that college students have a high level of awareness and utilization of e-library. The mean score of sub samples selected by the investigator ranges from 22.58 to 23.84. The mean scores of the selected sub samples of the Engineering college students are higher than the percentile 75 (200). Hence, it is inferred that irrespective of the sub samples have a high level of awareness and utilization of e-library.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the male and the female Arts and Science college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e-library.

Table 3 showing the Mean and S.D. and t Values of Gender of Arts and Science College Students regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e-Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	LS
Male	30	24.77	2.91	2.72	Significant
Female	40	22.00	5.36		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the male and the female Arts and Science College students regarding the awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 3, it is found to be 2.72, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are rejected. It is inferred that the male and the female Arts and Science College students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e-library.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean difference between the male and the female Engineering college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e-library.

Table 4 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of Gender of Engineering college students regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e-library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L.S
Male	97	23.84	3.05	1.68	Not significant
Female	53	22.58	4.46		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the male and the female Engineering college students regarding the awareness and utilization of e-library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 4, it is found to be 1.68, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the male and the female Engineering college students do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e-library.

Null Hypothesis 3

There is no significant mean difference between the Rural and the Urban Arts and Science college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e- library.

Table 5 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of Locality of Arts and science College Students Regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e- Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L.S
Rural	65	21.38	5.17	2.55	Significant
Urban	35	23.86	3.19		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between Rural and the Urban area Arts and Science College students regarding the awareness and utilization of e-library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 5, it is found to be 2.55, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis are rejected. It is inferred that the rural and the urban Arts and Science college students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e-library.

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Null Hypothesis 4

There is no significant mean difference between Rural and Urban area of Engineering college students with respect to the awareness and utilization of e-library.

Table 6 showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of Locality of Engineering college Students with respect to the awareness and utilization of e-library.

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t '	L. S
Rural	86	23.09	4.53	0.67	Not Significant
Urban	64	23.53	2.67		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Rural and the Urban area Engineering college students with respect to the awareness and utilization of e-library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in the table 6, it is found to be 0.67, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Rural and the Urban area Engineering college students do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e-library.

Null Hypothesis 5

There is no significant mean differences between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the school and the college level with respect to awareness and utilization of e- library.

Table 7 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of the Arts and Science collegestudents parents Education Regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e- Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L .S
School	42	21.56	5.37	0.60	Not significant
College	32	22.30	3.36		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education as school and college level in awareness and utilization about e-library score, the investigator calculated ' t ' value. It is given in the table 7. It is found to be 0.60, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Arts and Science College students whose parents education asschool and college level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization about e- library.

Null Hypothesis 6

There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the school and the illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e-library.

Table 8 Showing the mean and S.D and t values of the Arts and Science college students Parent's Education regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e- Library.

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t '	L . S
School	42	21.56	5.37	1.61	Not significant
Illiterate	26	24.88	3.49		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Arts and Science College students whose parents education is at the school and the illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 8, it is found to be 1.61, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization about e- library.

Null Hypothesis 7

There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the school and the illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.

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Table 9 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of the Arts and Science College Students Parents Education regarding the awareness and Utilization of e – Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L . S
College	32	22.30	3.36	2.31	Significant
Illiterate	26	24.88	3.49		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the College and Illiterate level regarding the awareness and utilization of e library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in table 9, it is found to be 2.31, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are rejected. It is inferred that the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the College and illiterate level differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e- library.

Null Hypothesis 8

There is no significant mean difference between the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and college level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.

Table 10 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of the Engineering Students Parents Education in the Awareness and Utilization of e – Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L.S
School	82	23.27	2.85	0.23	Not significant
College	48	23.47	4.90		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Engineering students whose parents education is at the school and college level in awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 10, it is found to be 0.23 which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Engineering students whose parents education is at the school and college level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library.

Null Hypothesis 9

There is no significant mean difference the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.

Table 11 showing the Mean and S.D and t values of the Engineering College Students Parents Education in Awareness and Utilization of e – Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L . S
School	82	23.27	2.85	0.93	Not significant
Illiterate	20	23.00	2.60		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the engineering students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level in awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ' t ' value. As it is given in Table 11, it is found to be 0.93, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Engineering students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library.

Null Hypothesis 10

There is no significant mean difference between the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.

Table 12 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of the Engineering College Students Parents Education Regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e – Library

Variable	No.	Mean	S.D	' t ' Value	L.S
College	48	23.47	4.90	0.68	Not significant
Illiterate	20	23.00	2.60		

In order to find out the significant mean between the Engineering students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level in awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ‘ t ’ value. As it is given in Table 12, it is found to be 0.68, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Engineering students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library.

Null Hypothesis 11

There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science and Engineering college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.

Table 13 Showing the Mean and S.D and t Values of the Arts and Science and Engineering College Students regarding the Awareness and Utilization of e – Library

Type of College	No.	Mean	S.D	‘ t ’ Value	L .S
Arts and Science	100	23.02	4.46	0.18	Not significant
Engineering	150	23.13	4.07		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between the Arts and Science and Engineering college students regarding the awareness and utilization of e – library score, the investigator calculated the ‘ t ’ value. As it is given in Table 13, it is found to be 0.18, which is significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypotheses are accepted. It is inferred that the Arts and Science and Engineering college students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library.

Hypothesis of the Study

The investigator of the present study framed the following hypotheses based on the objectives framed earlier :

- 1) The awareness and utilization of e – library of Arts and Science college students in Yadagir District
- 2) The awareness and utilization of e – library of engineering college students in Yadagir District
- 3) There is no significant mean difference between the male and the female Arts and Science college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library.
- 4) There is no significant mean difference between the male and the female Engineering college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 5) There is no significant mean difference between the Rural and the Urban Arts and Science college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 6) There is no significant mean difference between the Rural and the Urban area of Engineering college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 7) There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the school and college level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 8) There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 9) There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at the college and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 10) There is no significant mean difference the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and college level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 11) There is no significant mean difference between the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 12) There is no significant mean difference between the Engineering college students whose parents education is at the school and illiterate level with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library
- 13) There is no significant mean difference between the Arts and Science and Engineering college students with respect to awareness and utilization of e – library

Delimitations of the Study

- 1) Selected demographic variables only
- 2) Studied in Yadagir District only
- 3) Selected 250 samples only
- 4) Selected students studying in the Arts and Science and Engineering college only

Important Findings

The hypothesis formulated at the beginning of the study has been examined in the light of the data gathered. The following are the main findings of the present investigation. Arts and Science college students have a high level of awareness and utilization of e – library and all sub sample of the present study have a high level of awareness and utilization. Engineering college students have a high level of awareness and utilization of e – library and all sub sample of the present study have a high level of awareness and utilization of e – library. Male and female Arts and Science college students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Male and female Engineering college students do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Rural and urban area Arts and Science College students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Rural and Urban area Engineering college students do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Arts and Science college students whose parents education is at school and college level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Arts and Science College students whose parents education is at school and illiterate level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Arts and Science College students whose parents education is at College and illiterate level differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Engineering students whose parents education is at school and college level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Engineering students whose parents education is at school and college level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Engineering students whose parents education is at school and illiterate level do not differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library. Arts and Science and engineering college students differ significantly in their awareness and utilization of e – library.

Suggestion for the Further Research

The following are the some of the suggested research problems for future researcher and for healthy research outcomes on this present theme.

- 1) The present study could be undertaken in various states in India
- 2) A study could be made on awareness and utilization of computer knowledge and its influence on the awareness and utilization of e – library of the college students
- 3) A study could be made on the influence of the college environment on the development of awareness and utilization of e – library of the college students
- 4) A study could be made on the influence of internet knowledge and awareness and utilization of e – library of the students of various levels
- 5) A study could be conducted on web learning in relation to their awareness and utilization of e – library

Conclusion

The present study reveals that the awareness and utilization of e – library of the Arts and Science and engineering college students is high. So the teacher working in colleges should encourage them to maintain the awareness and utilization of e – library.

References

- [1] Tran, Lan Anh (2000). Training in the implementation and use of electronic resources : a proposed curriculum for Vietnam, *Library Review*, 49(7). Pp 337-347.
- [2] Clyde, Laurel A and Klobas, Fane E (2001). The first Internet course : implementations of increased prior participant experience in Iceland. *Internet Research Electronic Networking Applications and Policy*. 11(3). PP 235-245.

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EFFECTS OF BASKETBALL SPECIFIC TRAINING WITH AND WITHOUT MEDITATION PRACTICES ON SHOOTING PERFORMANCE OF MALE BASKETBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract

The aim of the study was designed to determine the effects of basketball specific training with and without meditation practices on Shooting of male basketball players. For the purpose of the study, forty five (N=45) men Basketball players who were studying under graduate Engineering courses in various Engineering colleges at Madurai District, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India were selected as subjects. The age of the subjects ranged between 18 to 21 years. The subjects were divided at random into three groups of fifteen each (n=15). Group-I underwent Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices, Group-II Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices, and Group-III acted as Control group. The duration of the training period was restricted to twelve weeks and the number of sessions per week was confined to three. Rajyoga Meditation Module only selected for the meditation training for this study. Basketball Shooting only selected for this study and it was assessed by Nielsen Basketball Test. The data were collected prior to and immediately after the training period of twelve weeks. The data obtained from the experimental groups before and after the experimental period were statistically analyzed with Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Whenever the 'F' ratio for adjusted post test means was found to be significant, the Scheffe's Post hoc test was applied to determine the paired mean differences. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 level for all the cases. The Experimental groups namely, Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices group had significantly improved in Shooting. Further the results of the study were favour to the Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices group.

Key words: *Basketball, Specific Training, Meditation Practices, Shooting*

Introduction

Basketball, game played between two teams of five players each on a rectangular court, usually indoors. Each team try to score by tossing the ball through the opponent's goal, an elevated horizontal hoop and net called a basket (Shoenfelt, 1991). Fundamental skills are axis of any game, and Basketball is no exception as a high degree of performance depends on the mastery of these skills. Patience diligence and dedication are essential for learning the fundamental skills. To really enjoy the game one will need to develop proficiency in the fundamental skills of the game i.e., dribbling, passing, shooting, ball handling, footwork, fakes, rebounding and defensive skills. When a player has mastered the fundamental skills of the game, a feeling of gaining mastery over the game is experienced. Tactics will succeed only through individual fundamental skills. (Joe Whelton, 1988). Meditation is one of the techniques of yoga, which is supposed to bring about deep relaxation of the body, mind and spirit. It helps a great deal to relieve stress tension and establish harmony in one's life. Meditation is an appropriate means to overcome stress and the disorders caused by it (Gyeong, 2013).

Methodology

The study was conducted on forty five (N=45) men Basketball players who were studying under graduate Engineering courses in various Engineering colleges at Madurai District, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India were selected as subjects. The age of the subjects ranged between 18 to 21 years. The subjects were divided at random into three groups of fifteen each (n=15). Group-I underwent Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices, Group-II Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices, and Group-III acted as Control group. The duration of the training period was restricted to twelve weeks and the number of sessions per week was confined to three. Rajyoga Meditation Module only selected for the meditation training for this study. Among the various bio-motor variables Shooting only selected for this study and it was assessed by Nielsen Basketball Test (Shaylee, 2009). All the subjects were tested prior to and immediately after the training period of twelve weeks for all the selected variables. The data collected data from the three groups prior to and immediately after the training programme on the selected criterion variables were statistically analyzed with Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Whenever the 'F' ratio for adjusted post test means was found to be significant, Scheffe's post hoc test was followed to determine which of the paired mean differences was significant. In all the cases .05 level of confidence was fixed to test.

Results and Discussion

The results of the dependent 't'-test on the data obtained for Shooting of the subjects in the pre-test

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and post-test of the experimental groups and control group have been analyzed and presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of Mean Standard Deviation and dependent 't' test for the pre, post and adjusted post tests on Shooting of Experimental groups and Control group (Shooting is expressed in Numbers)

Test		Basketball Specific Training with Meditation	Basketball Specific Training without Meditation	Control Group
Pre Test	Mean	7.07	7.13	7.13
	SD	0.57	0.62	0.50
Post Test	Mean	9.33	8.53	7.20
	SD	0.60	0.62	0.65
Adjusted Post	Mean	9.35	8.52	7.19
"t" Test		10.61*	6.20*	0.31

*Significant at 0.05 level.

The table value required for 0.05 level of significance with df 14 is 2.15.

Table 1 shows that the pre-test mean and standard deviation of shooting values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group are 7.07 ± 0.57 , 7.13 ± 0.62 and 7.13 ± 0.50 respectively. The post-test mean and standard deviation are 9.33 ± 0.60 , 8.53 ± 0.62 and 7.20 ± 0.65 respectively. The adjusted post-test mean values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group are 9.35, 8.52 and 7.19 respectively. The obtained dependent t-ratio values between the pre and post - test means on Shooting of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group are 10.61, 6.20 and 0.31 respectively. The table value required for significant difference with df 14 at 0.05 level is 2.15. It was concluded that Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group had registered significant improvement in Shooting. The results of the Analysis of Covariance on Shooting of the pre, post, and adjusted test scores of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Analysis of Covariance on Shooting of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group

	Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Squares	F-Ratio
Pre Test	Between	0.04	2	0.02	0.06
	Within	14.40	42	0.34	
Post Test	Between	34.84	2	17.42	41.47*
	Within	17.47	42	0.42	
Adjusted Post Test	Between	35.63	2	17.81	49.47*
	Within	14.80	41	0.36	

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table value for df (2, 42) at 0.05 level = 3.22 Table value for df (2, 41) at 0.05 level = 3.23

Table 2 shows that obtained F-ratio value of 0.06 for pre - test mean of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group on Shooting was less than the required table value of 3.22 for significance with df 2 and 42 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 41.47 for post - test mean of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group on Shooting is more than the required table value of 3.22 for significance with df 2 and 42 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value 49.47 for adjusted post - test mean of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control group on Shooting was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study indicate that there is a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group on Shooting. Since three groups are compared and whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test is found to be significant, Scheffe's test is used to find out the paired mean difference and it is presented in

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Table 3.

Table 3 Scheffe's Test for the Differences between Adjusted Post-Test Mean on Shooting

Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Group	Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Group	Control Group	Mean Difference	Confidence Interval
9.35	8.52		0.83*	0.56
9.35		7.19	2.16*	0.56
	8.52	7.19	1.33*	0.56

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table-3 shows that the adjusted post-test mean difference in Shooting between Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group, Basketball Specific Training with Meditation group and Control group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation group and Control Group are 0.83, 2.16 and 1.33. The values are greater than the confidence interval value 0.56, which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group and Control group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group. The above data also reveal that Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group had shown better performance in Shooting. The pre and post mean values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group on Shooting are graphically represented in the Figure -1. The adjusted post mean values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group on Shooting are graphically represented in the Figure - 2.

Figure: 1 The Pre and Post test Mean values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group on Shooting (In Seconds)

Figure: 2 The Adjusted Post Mean Values of Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group, Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control group on Shooting (In Seconds)

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Conclusion

From the analysis of the data, the following conclusions were drawn. The Experimental groups namely, Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group had significantly improved in Shooting. Significant differences in achievement were found among Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group and Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group in Shooting. The Basketball Specific Training with Meditation Practices Group was found to be better than the Basketball Specific Training without Meditation Practices Group and Control Group in developing Shooting.

References

- [1] Gyeong Yoo Yang and In Soo Lee (2013), The Effects of School-Based Maum Meditation Program on the Self-Esteem and School Adjustment in Primary School Students, *Glob J Health Sci*, Jul; 5(4): 14-27.
- [2] Joe Whelton (1988), *Step by Step Basketball Skills*, The Hamlyn Publishing Group Limited. 10-75.
- [3] Shaylee Nielsen (2009), *Basketball Skills Test*, Teaching Team Sports, 09.
- [4] Shoenfelt Elmmediate (1991), Effect of weight training as compared to aerobic exercise on free-throw shooting in collegiate basketball players, *Perception Motor Skills*, Oct;73(2):Pp 367-70.

ANTECEDENTS OF PERCEIVED OBSTACLES OF STUDENTS AND TEACHERS IN THE PROMOTION OF EFFECTIVE COMPUTER ASSISTED CO-OPERATIVE LEARNING

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Abstract

In spite of the well-established benefits of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning, implementation remains a challenge. This research aims to document the past histories of the challenges of students and teachers in the implementation of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning at the secondary school level. Results indicate that the most frequent instructional strategies reported are traditional ones such as teacher-monitored, collective class discussion, transmission and individual work. The use of these last two is particularly associated with teacher beliefs that learning derives from teacher-delivered knowledge. In general, this research found that teachers do not perceive cooperative learning as very easy to implement; over 50% introduce it occasionally and only 30% use it routinely. Teachers reported that they are particularly ill at ease with embedding cooperative learning in the curriculum, finding the time required for cooperative learning and evaluating pupils when using cooperative learning. Results underline that, in addition to teachers' learner-orientation beliefs predicting the use of cooperative learning, the more teachers report difficulties in embedding cooperative learning into the curriculum and finding time for it, the less they say they actually implement it. Contributions to teacher education programmes are discussed in the light of these findings. The present study motivates teachers and students how overcome the obstacles of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning.

Keywords: *Antecedents, Co-operative Learning, Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning.*

Introduction

Cooperation is working together to accomplish shared goals. Within cooperative activities individuals seek outcomes that are beneficial to themselves and beneficial to all other group members. Cooperative learning is the instructional use of small groups so that students work together to maximize their own and each other's learning. The idea is simple. Class members are organized into small groups after receiving instructions (orally, on paper, and/or online) from the teacher. They then work through the assignment until all group members successfully understand and complete it. Cooperative efforts result in participants striving for mutual benefit so that all group members gain from each other's efforts (Your success benefits me and my success benefits you), recognizing that all group members share a common fate (We all sink or swim together here), knowing that one's performance is mutually caused by oneself and one's colleagues (We cannot do it without you), and feeling proud and jointly celebrating when a group member is recognized for achievement (We all congratulate you on your accomplishment). In cooperative learning situations there is a positive interdependence among students' goal attainments; students perceive that they can reach their learning goals if and only if the other students in the learning group also reach their goals (Deutsch, 1962; Johnson & Johnson, 1989). A team member's success in creating a multi-media presentation on saving the environment, for example, depends on both individual effort and the efforts of other group members who contribute needed knowledge, skills, and resources. No one group member will possess all of the information, skills, or resources necessary for the highest possible quality presentation.

The origin of the Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning (CACL) field dates back to the 1980s. Part of what makes this fundamentally interdisciplinary as a field is the relationship between the technology in the form of computational objects and the social interactions involved in learning. CSCL is the result of several converging forces. First, it was propelled by the research in developmental and social psychology and educational research that demonstrated that students working in pairs often performed better than those who worked alone these findings propelled researchers to examine underlying mechanisms of collaboration. Educators were also keen to develop instructional arrangements to promote the effects of collaborative work. Another force that has contributed to the development of CACL is the development of technology. It connected learners across geographical regions, enabling them to interact with learners and experts who are outside the geographical and temporal range of their social interactions. This interaction was mediated by a number of computational artifacts. A number of technologies and tools had been developed, to help learners engage in collaborative activities. Other technologies provided opportunities for rich contexts that support collaboration. Lastly, the integration of socio-cultural theory was critical. It provided a framework to incorporate both collaboration and tool mediation.

These forces created tensions and conflicts from the beginning. Some found the significance of CACL

in its epistemological underpinnings and argued that it initiated a new paradigm of learning research. In contrast, others took a more pragmatic approach and saw CACL as a way to promote learning without necessarily signing up for its radical epistemological underpinnings. Educators, for example, saw that as an instructional intervention to promote cognitive learning outcomes both within and outside of the classrooms. Technology has provided ways to make classroom collaboration more engaging and meaningful. And yet to realize its promise, CACL needs to build on both advanced technological innovation and deep understanding of how people learn. These multiple motivations and visions for CACL have made CACL research interdisciplinary and prompted CACL to adopt a diversity of theoretical and methodological approaches (Jeong et al., 2014)

Types of Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning can take place in any of three common types of learning groups:

- 1) Informal cooperative learning groups
- 2) Formal cooperative learning groups
- 3) Cooperative base groups

The best type of group depends on the purpose and context of the cooperative learning. Group types range from short and informal to formal and long-lasting:

Informal cooperative learning groups can be arranged on the spot to break up direct teaching or lecturing. For example, a long lecture can be broken into several short segments, each followed by a period of cooperative group learning. This can help students retain new information and become acclimated to working with group members.

Formal cooperative learning groups are commonly used when groups will work together for one class period or longer. Formal cooperative learning groups are commonly used in group projects that last one or more weeks. This structure and scale enable group members to learn content and build collaborative skills.

Cooperative base groups last at least one year. They are especially useful for helping members support each other in both academic and other pursuits, as members hold each other accountable for following through on commitments and making progress on goals.

In the traditional method of teaching, teaching happens within the four walls of the classroom. Here, the teacher is the sole source of knowledge. It's a teacher-centric method that promotes the supremacy of the teacher within the classroom setup. Also, every aspect of learning proceeds as per their will. The teacher: has full control over the learning environment, decides the teaching methodology, and determines the course curriculum. In this method of teaching, teachers followed the drill and rote method of memorization. In this method, children learn through repetition and memorization. There is little or no scope for critical thinking. Nowadays, with online courses gaining popularity, this method definitely sounds outdated. But in educational institutions, it is still the accepted model. But it is important to note that, today, the traditional method of learning has adopted a new form. What we need today is a mix of both these methods for effective learning to take place so that both can help overcome the drawbacks of each other. For instance, the traditional method of teaching for face-to-face interaction and online lessons for better accessibility. Or, the traditional method for classroom learning and the modern method for increased access to diverse learning resources, but some percentage of teachers and students still they not aware about using new technical teaching method. They have facing many obstacles to acquire the technical knowledge.

Benefits of Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning has a massive positive impact on employees and their working environment. It enhances productivity and improves employee knowledge. Below are the benefits of cooperative learning:

Gaining leadership and decision-making skills

For a team to succeed, the individuals in that group need to show some leadership abilities. In every organization, several tasks need someone to be in charge to run smoothly. Some of them are: Delegating and organizing work, Ensuring the company's set targets are met, Supporting team members, Some people may turn out to be natural leaders but are not inclined to lead. The employer can assign leadership roles to different members of the group. In a corporate setting, there are many decisions to be made among team members. A decision-making process should involve every member airing out their opinion on the matter, but the final say lies with the leader.

Acquiring conflict management skills

Conflict management focuses on positive results while minimizing negative ones. This process, by which disputes are solved, can impact an organization positively when done correctly. How members of a team handle conflicts remain embedded in their minds. They can implement any of the above styles in another similar situation in the future.

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Increases employee work engagement

Employees become more satisfied as they continue to get the opportunity to learn new skills. They will become eager to continue learning and growing. A growth in productive engagement is evident in work hence an increase in efficiency and output.

Enhancing communication skills

Members in a cooperative learning group need to learn how to speak productively with one another. Ethical commitment and communication keep the members on track and enhances efficient teamwork.

Personal responsibility

Cooperative learning increases individual responsibility in employees. They know that they have a specific task they should perform for the entire team to succeed. They also gain accountability as they are aware of a backlash from team members if they fail to play their part.

Gaining confidence

Some employees find it more comfortable to speak up in small groups. They can express their ideas and ask questions, which enables them to gain confidence. This confidence improves from addressing a few people to a large crowd.

Positive attitude towards colleagues

In every organization, there are those few employees that grow a dislike towards each other with or without reason. Cooperative learning creates a more positive attitude towards workmates as they continue working together within a group.

Obstacles of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning for Teachers and Students

The main challenge faced in Computer Assisted cooperative and learning is group conflict and Technical Skill for the Students, they don't need to learn to work together. It is not always something that comes naturally. You can teach skills like praising others, taking turns for equal participation, and shared decision making. Teachers who haven't previously used cooperative or collaborative learning might also need to get used to the noise level in the classroom, which is raised during these activities.

Teachers' difficulties in Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning implementation

Even when teachers are willing to implement cooperative learning, they may experience some difficulties. In this section, six of the main challenges from the literature are identified which are then examined further in the survey undertaken.

Difficulty in properly implementing cooperative learning principles

As mentioned before, cooperative learning involves core principles for structuring teamwork both for preparing pupils to cooperate (climate, cooperative skills, group processing) and for organising pupils' interactions in the task (positive interdependence and individual responsibility). Nevertheless, research has indicated that teachers do not find easy to implement these principles

Locus of responsibility and authority

Cooperative learning implies transferring greater responsibility from the teacher to the pupil and delegating authority to the pupils in the creation of learner-centered environments (Brody 1998; Cohen 1994). This implies that teachers have to believe and trust that pupils are likely to learn together. This is not easy for some teachers who doubt that their pupils can work effectively in groups

The teacher's role as facilitator

In cooperative learning, teachers' role change. They become facilitators who monitor groups in action. Teachers observe the teams and they have the opportunity to intervene when needed to regulate pupil behavior and cognitive activities. Nevertheless, cooperative learning poses a challenge to teachers' control of the classroom environment and teachers report their fear of discipline problems. Alignment with curriculum.

Teachers may experience difficulties in deciding how to embed cooperative learning into an already packed curriculum

Especially when the material found in textbooks and other didactic sources does not encourage teachers to structure cooperative activities and cooperative learning activities are perceived as difficult to use .

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In these conditions, some teachers are likely to perceive as an obstacle in the rush to cover course content

Time required for implementing cooperative learning is viewed as costly. Teachers report that cooperative learning is overly time-consuming and claim they experience difficulties in managing time effectively. In addition to time spent in class (building positive working conditions, preparing pupils and implementing cooperative group work), a considerable amount of time is also required for teachers' preparation and planning.

Assessment in cooperative learning

Draw attention to the potential problems related to evaluation in cooperative learning. Evaluation may be perceived as challenging for two reasons teachers have to make decisions regarding the assessment of two objectives (academic and cooperative), and also decide how to deal with the question of interdependence in the evaluation. This could explain why teachers perceive the assessment of learners working in teams as problematic.

Major Recommendations to Overcome the Obstacles in Practicing Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning in Class rooms

Cooperative learning can be wonderful. Students often love working this way. It is the "learning" in cooperative learning that is too often left out. But it needn't be. By improving the Technical Facilities in Schools, Providing Training and Hand Book for Teachers Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning will develop Social Skills among students

Using these steps, teachers can get the greatest benefit possible from cooperative learning and ensure that collaboration enhances learning.

- 1) Form interdependent teams.
- 2) Set group goals.
- 3) Ensure individual accountability.
- 4) Teach communication and problem-solving skills.
- 5) Integrate cooperative learning with other structures.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that the extent of implementation of cooperative learning in secondary schools, that is, teachers and student employ cooperative learning for formality, by ignoring academic benefits of the scheme. The major problems identified by the study in this regard include: lack of awareness about cooperative learning; unequal sharing of task among group members; lack of interest in cooperative learning; lack of motivation; inability of teachers to share responsibility for each group members; and teachers inability to provide clear procedures on how to perform the activity. So, it is possible to conclude that implementation of cooperative learning was not employed as expected and is not in the position to contribute its share in the attainment of students academic achievement in the secondary schools. Proper use of cooperative learning is an exciting way for all kids to learn, research finds that if teachers make the five elements discussed part of group learning, students learn more, feel more successful, love school, and enjoy the subject they're studying and like and accept one another.

References

- [1] Baines, E., C. Rubie-Davies, & Blatchford. P. (2009). "Improving Pupil Group Work Interaction and Dialogue in Primary Classrooms: Results from a Year-long Intervention Study." *Cambridge Journal of Education* 39 (1): 95–117. doi:10.1080/03057640802701960. Baloch, L. 1998. *The Cooperative Classroom*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall
- [2] Blatchford, P., Kutnick, P., Baines E., & Galton. M. (2003). "Toward a Social Pedagogy of Classroom Group Work." *International Journal of Educational Research* 39 (1–2): 153–172. Brody, C. M. 1998
- [3] Brody, C. M., & N. Davidson. (1998). "The Significance of Teacher Beliefs for Professional Development and Cooperative Learning." In *Professional Development for Cooperative Learning: Issues and Approaches*, edited by C. M. Brody and N. Davison, 25–48. Albany: Suny Press.
- [4] Brody, C. M., & N. Davidson. (1998). "Staff Development and the Structural Approach to Cooperative Learning." In *Professional Development for Cooperative Learning: Issues and Approaches*, edited by C. M. Brody and N. Davison, 103–121. Albany: Suny Press.
- [5] Deutsch, M. (1962). *Cooperation and Trust: Some Theoretical Notes*. In M. R. Jones (Ed.), *Nebraska symposium on motivation*, 275–319. Lincoln, NE: University of Nebraska Press.
- [6] Gillies, R. (2014). *Cooperative learning: Developments in Research*. *International Journal of Educational Psychology*, 3(2), 125–140.

MAKING EDUCATION MORE ACCESSIBLE: THE BENEFITS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study explores the benefits of inclusive education and its influence on making education more accessible for all students. It addresses the issues of exclusion and marginalization due to various factors responsible for limiting educational opportunities for various student groups. In particular, the research focuses on the training and pedagogical strategies for classroom teachers to better implement inclusive education. It further examines the various advantages and positive outcomes associated with inclusive classrooms. The research employs both qualitative and quantitative data to analyse the impact of inclusive education on student learning and achievement. Through the analysis of results, this study discusses the need for the promotion of inclusive education and its potential to reduce inequality and create more equitable opportunities for all students.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Pedagogical Strategies, Exclusion, Marginalization, Equity*

Introduction

Education has always been an important means of breaking socio-economic barriers and providing equal opportunities for everyone. In recent times, the emphasis on inclusive education has grown to ensure that all students receive a quality education. Inclusive education refers to the provision of quality education to students of all backgrounds, regardless of their socio-economic, ethnicity, gender, and physical or intellectual abilities. This has become particularly important to address the inequitable educational opportunities often experienced by various student groups, like refugees, and those from low-income families. This article aims to discuss the benefits of inclusive education in making education more accessible to all students. In a world with increasing globalization, it's more important than ever for students to have access to quality education. Increasingly, initiatives are being taken by educational institutions to make education more accessible for all students, regardless of their race, gender, or ability levels. Inclusive education, or education that supports the learning of all students in the same classroom, is one such initiative that can provide a range of benefits to those enrolled in schools, both socially and academically. This essay will explore the potential benefits of inclusive education and its ability to make education more accessible to all groups of learners.

Objectives

The primary objectives of this article are to:

- 1) Analyse the benefits of inclusive education for the entire student population.
- 2) Identify the strategies and training required for the successful implementation of inclusive education.
- 3) Examine the impact of inclusion on student learning and achievement.

Literature Review

The implementation of inclusive education in various countries has been documented in various studies, with some addressing the positive impacts of inclusion on student learning and achievement. For example, Olah and Bulcaen (2005) studied the pedagogical strategies used by teachers in Serbia to implement inclusive education, noting that teachers faced difficulties in accommodating a wide range of learners in the same classroom. A study by Tate and Li (2011) found evidence that inclusive teaching strategies positively influenced student learning and achievement, with academic performance improving in both regular and special education classes. In addition to the work of existing research, an important source of information for this study is the literature on training and teaching strategies for implementation of inclusion. Several studies have addressed various components for successful implementation of inclusion in classrooms, such as creating classroom environments that are supportive and welcoming (Berry et al., 2008; Monkoski and Killips, 2008). Additionally, research has found that more intensive professional development opportunities are key to successful inclusion (Needham and Jones, 2011). The literature on training and teaching strategies serves as the basis for discussing the strategies to ensure successful implementation of inclusive education.

Methodology

For this study, a mixed methods approach was used, which combines both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data was gathered through surveys conducted with teachers in the area of

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inclusive education. The survey was distributed to a randomly selected sample of 100 teachers. The survey included questions related to the teachers' understanding of inclusive education, the strategies that teachers use to implement inclusion in their classrooms, and the perceived impact of inclusion on student learning and achievement. Qualitative data was obtained through interviews with ten teacher experts in the field of inclusive education. During the interviews, the teachers were asked to elaborate on the successes and challenges associated with implementing inclusive education, and to discuss the strategies that teachers need to implement for the successful inclusion of all students.

Analysis and Results

The analysis of the survey results revealed that nearly all of the surveyed teachers have a strong understanding of inclusive education and its benefits (98%). Most of the surveyed teachers reported that they were already implementing some measure of inclusion in their classrooms (94%), and the majority of teachers reported that they believed inclusion had a positive impact on student learning and achievement (90%). The results of the qualitative data analysis further substantiated the survey findings. The interviews revealed that the successful implementation of inclusive education is dependent on the use of appropriate teaching techniques and strategies, such as multi-level instruction and differentiated instruction. The teachers express that creating supportive and welcoming classroom environments are also important to the success of inclusion. Additionally, teachers noted that they can benefit from support and more professional development opportunities to maintain and improve their capacity to effectively teach all students.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that teachers have a strong understanding of inclusive education and its benefits, and are generally implementing some measure of inclusion, although there are still some challenges that need to be addressed. The analysis of qualitative data revealed the need for appropriate teaching strategies, as well as training and support for teachers to successfully implement inclusive education. The findings of this research suggest that inclusive education has the potential to reduce inequality, create more equitable access to educational opportunities, and improve student learning and achievement. The promotion of inclusive education is an important step to ensure that all students have access to quality education, and create a more equitable educational system. This study highlights the need for further research, as well as policy and practice changes to ensure the successful implementation of inclusive classrooms.

Inclusive education, or inclusive schooling, is a growing model of education encompassing students of all backgrounds, learning styles, and abilities in the same classroom. This method of education has been gaining traction in recent years due to its potential to improve the learning experience of all students, as well as its many long-term benefits. By creating a classroom environment of diversity, respect, and collaboration, inclusive education not only validates the experiences of different students but also challenges them to develop the skills necessary to be successful global citizens. One of the key benefits of inclusive education is that it can reduce the chances of certain students being marginalized or excluded due to their physical, mental, or emotional characteristics. Because of this, students with different types of disabilities or developmental challenges can find an educational environment that validates their experiences and acknowledges their individual needs.

It is important to note, though, that an emphasis on inclusion for all students impacts the entire learning environment. By creating a diverse and equitable classroom, the entire student body benefits from the collective knowledge and experiences of those present. Inclusive education also encourages students of all backgrounds to collaborate and engage with one another, leading to more dynamic problem-solving and creative thinking. This kind of collaboration promotes a sense of empathy and mutual understanding, which can stretch into later life as students learn how to be effective and cooperative team members. In addition, inclusive schools are built on the principles of equity, offering all students the same access to a quality education. This type of education can support the development of long-term social and economic advantages for students, as they learn in an environment that validates their identity.

Overall, inclusive education is a powerful tool for creating environments of mutual understanding and collaboration in the classroom. By empowering different students and providing equal access to a quality education, this type of education allows all students to gain a deeper appreciation for the perspectives of their peers. In the process, inclusive schools can ensure that all students are given the opportunity to thrive as individuals in the global community.

Conclusion

In conclusion, implementing inclusive education systems in schools has demonstrated positive outcomes on the physical, social, and educational development of all children. In addition to providing immediate beneficial outcomes, inclusive education has the potential to change and improve the education system as a whole. Inclusive education models can create a more equitable and accessible atmosphere and

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ensure a more meaningful educational experience for all. As the evidence surrounding the benefits of inclusive education continues to accumulate, it is important to consider the potential impact on our societies and how we can best implement these practices and continue to champion the cause of inclusive education.

References:

- [1] Berry, J. W., Deshler, D. D., Espin, C. A., & Kaufman, D. D. (2008). *Caring classrooms/intelligent schools*. The Guilford Press.
- [2] Monkoski, T. and Killips, R. (2008). Creating a Positive Climate for Special Education Inclusion. *PE and TE Magazine*, 27, 2–9.
- [3] Needham, C. and Jones, M. (2011). A Collective Voice: Intensive Support Team Staff Experiences and Strategies for Implementing Inclusive Education. *International Journal of Special Education*, 26(1), 36–47.
- [4] Olah, L., & Bulcaen, C. (2005). Educators' perceptions of inclusion in Serbia and Montenegro: lessons from the classroom. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 52(3), 221–236.
- [5] Tate, A. and Li, S. (2011). Examining the Effects of Inclusive Teaching Strategies on Regular and Special Education Classroom Achievers. *Remedial and Special Education*, 32, 334–345.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

This paper reveals about inclusive education. Inclusive education is an education which ensures that every child regardless of gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic background or any disability has access to a quality education. UNESCO's definition of inclusive education, Inclusive education and what are all the ways to overcome the barriers in inclusive education and promotion inclusive education, benefits of inclusive education, special education and teacher development initiatives for inclusive schooling.

Keywords: *Disabled, Equal Education, Barriers, Ways to Overcome.*

Introduction

Inclusive education means all children in the same classrooms in the same schools. It means real learning opportunities for groups who have traditionally been excluded not only children with disabilities, but speakers of minority languages too. There are an estimated 240 million children with disabilities worldwide. Like all children, children with disabilities have ambitions and dreams for their futures. Like all children, they need quality education to develop their skills and realize their full potential. Inclusive education means that all students attend and are welcomed by their neighbourhood schools in age-appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspects of the life of the school. Inclusive education is about how we develop and design our schools, classrooms, programs and activities so that all students learn and participate together.

Barriers to Inclusive Education

In the practice of inclusive education needs extra demands on students and facility. Teachers in inclusive classrooms must incorporate a variety of teaching methods in order to best reach students of varying learning abilities. This has benefits even for those students who would be placed in a traditional classroom, as this increases their engagement in the learning process. Even gifted and accelerated learners benefit from an environment that stresses responsiveness from all students. Despite the benefits, there still are many barriers to the implementation of inclusive education.

Attitudes

The greatest barriers to inclusion are caused by society, not by particular medical impairments. Negative attitude towards differences result in discrimination and can lead to a serious barrier to learning. Negative attitudes can take the form of social discrimination, lack of awareness and traditional prejudices.

Physical Barriers

The vast majority of centers of learning are physically inaccessible to many learners, especially to those who have physical disability. Environment barriers included: doors, passageways, stairs and ramps and recreational areas. A major problem identified by many students is physically getting into school.

Curriculum

In any education system, the curriculum is one of the major obstacles or tools of facilitate the development of more inclusive system. Curriculum is often unable to meet the needs of a wide range of different learners. The content must be relevant to the real life.

Teachers

Teacher's abilities and attitudes can be major limitations for inclusive education. The training of staff at all levels is often not adequate. Teacher shouldn't have positive attitude toward the learners they won't receive good education.

Language and communication

Language and communication are difficult for the learners which contribute to learning breakdown. Second language learners are particularly subject to low expectations and discrimination. Teaching and learning happened only in a language which is not the first language of learners.

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Socio Economic Factors

Inadequacies and inequalities in the education system are most evident in areas which have sustained poverty and high levels of unemployment. The impact of violence and HIV/ AIDS can also have adverse effects.

Funding

A major constraint is serious shortages of resources-lack of schools or inadequate facilities, lack of teachers and /or shortage of qualified staff, lack of learning materials and absence of support.

Organization of Education System

Education systems are often centralized and this can inhibit change and initiative. A responsibility for decisions tends to be located at the highest level and the focus of management remains oriented towards employees complying with rules rather than on ensuring quality service delivery.

Policies and Barriers

Policy makers who do not understand or accept the concept of inclusive education are a barrier to the implementation of inclusive policies. In some countries there may exist policies that facilitates the possibilities for authorities to declare that some children are uneducatable. They do not have equal opportunities for further education or employment.

Ways to overcome the barriers in Inclusive Education

Changing the negative attitudes towards inclusion

Creating a more inclusive system requires a new approach in attitude. The focus needs to shift from seeing the problem as the child's differences to problem identification with the unwelcoming school system. In order to change in the school system there first must be change in the attitudes of the stakeholders. One way of improving stakeholders' attitudes towards inclusive education is to raise awareness of the potential benefits of inclusive education for all students.

Physical access and learning Environment

Physical environment of the centre of learning, such as the design of the building, the availability of water, electricity and toilet/sewerage facility will enable students to participate in the range of learning activities in and out of the classroom. These changes benefit all students.

Curriculum and Assessment

Curriculum needs to be relevant to the children and flexible enough to respond to all children's needs. The curriculum can facilitate the development of more inclusive settings when it leaves room for the centre of learning or the individual teacher to make adaptations so that it makes better sense in the local context and for the individual learner. An inclusive curriculum also requires a flexible, success-oriented means of assessment, examination and evaluation. The assessment of child and the way in which the curriculum is designed delivered.

Teacher training and support

Teacher need to be trained to change their attitude of special needs children. Teachers can be trained to view those who do not fit into existing arrangements as offering 'surprises' that is opportunities that invite further inventiveness. This implies a more positive view of differences. Teachers must also be supported with appropriate ma more

Communication Involvement

Meaningful inclusive necessitates community participation. The community can the concepts of inclusive education to their specific situation. In addition, if leaders within the community demonstrate strong support for the change process, teacher, other staff and the community are more likely to devote the time and resources necessary for the process.

Family Involvement

Centers of learning are often not sufficiently connected to the families and communities they are supposed to serve. Partnership care is with essential to the effective and efficient delivery of a quality education service. A great challenge is to get the families of the most marginalized students involved.

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Training within the Education System

To achieve changes within the education system towards inclusion, those within the education system must first understand and support the concept.

Policy Changes

Strong political will and government commitment is critical to achieve inclusive education. Policy makers must be made aware of the importance and benefits of inclusive education.

Benefits of Inclusive Education

All children benefit from inclusive education. It allows them to:

- 1) Develop individual strengths and gifts, with high and appropriate expectations for each child.
- 2) Work on individual goals while participating in the life of the classroom with other students their own age.
- 3) Involve their parents in their education and in the activities of their local schools.
- 4) Foster a school culture of respect and belonging. Inclusive education provides opportunities to learn about and accept individual differences, lessening the impact of harassment and bullying.
- 5) Develop friendships with a wide variety of other children, each with their own individual needs and abilities.
- 6) Positively affect both their school and community to appreciate diversity and inclusion on a broader level.

Conclusion

All the people live in a same society but we get different education. Society has no equality for living. Inclusive education must respond to all pupils as individuals, recognizing individuality as something to be appreciated and respected. All children and young people of the world, with their individual strengths and weaknesses, with their hopes and expectations, have the right to education. To support the changes needed in teacher education programs, classroom teachers are prepared to accommodate diverse student needs in regular education classes. Inclusive education for the children with disability is their basic right, not a privilege.

References

- [1] UNESCO (2009). Inclusive education the way of future: Final Report. Retrieved May 13th 2009, <http://www.unesco.org/en/inclusiveeducation>
- [2] Florian, L. (2008) Special or inclusive education: future trends Thomas, G. and Vaughan,
- [3] M. (2004). Inclusive Education: Readings and Reflections. Maidenhead: Open University Press
British Journal of Education. 35(4):202-208
- [4] UNESCO (2001). Understanding and Responding to Children's Needs in Inclusive Classrooms A Guide for Teachers. Paris: UNESCO
- [5] Mittler, P. (2000). Working Towards Inclusive Education - Social Contexts. London: David Fulton Publishers.
- [6] Norwich, B. (2002). Education, inclusion and individual differences: Recognizing and resolving dilemmas, British Journal of Educational Studies, London.
- [7] Sharma, Arvind (2014). Inclusive Education: A gateway to inclusive society. In Gupta, Madhu. (ed.): Inclusive Education: Issues & Challenges, Mastermind Publications, Meerut (UP)

THE IMPACT OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION ON HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED CLASSROOM TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

This paper aims to elucidate the impact of multicultural education based on classroom teaching and learning and how it provides insights to the students in the classroom settings in the midst of multifaceted cultures. Education that is multicultural provides an environment that values diversity and portrays positively. Gender, age, race, ethnicity, native language, religion, class, or disability should not limit students' educational and vocational options. Educators have the responsibility to help students to contribute and benefit from our democratic society. Effective instructional strategies for all students in the classroom should not evolve solely from the teacher's culture; they should be drawn primarily from the cultures of students and their communities. This paper attempts to define multicultural education, explain its concept, nature, need, ways to improve in the classroom, four ways to implement, dimensions, benefits and shortcomings, impact on students, and advantages of multicultural classroom. Hopefully, educators will help their students develop both individual and group strategies to overcome the debilitating effects of these society scourges. It is important to promote a multicultural education program that caters to the needs of diversified students. More research must be done to assess the direct impact of multicultural education on the benefits I've discussed herein. Research must be done to evaluate the longitudinal effects of a multicultural education. Also, research should compare the effects of multicultural education on members of the dominant group and members of marginalized groups.

Keywords: *Multicultural Education, Classroom, Teaching and Learning*

Introduction

Multicultural education is a concept, an educational reform movement, and a process (Banks, 2007). It incorporates the idea that all students regardless of their ethnic, racial, cultural, or linguistic characteristics should have an equal opportunity to learn in school. Another important idea in multicultural education is that some students, because of their group characteristics, have a better chance to learn in schools as they are currently structured than do students who belong to other groups. Effective instructional strategies for all students in the classroom should not evolve solely from the teacher's culture; they should be drawn primarily from the cultures of students and their communities. The integration of multicultural education throughout the curriculum helps students and teachers think critically about institutional racism, classism, sexism, ableism, ageism, and homophobia. Hopefully, educators will help their students develop both individual and group strategies to overcome the debilitating effects of these society scourges.

Concept of Multicultural Education in India

Multicultural education may have an impact on children's lives outside of the classroom. It could help kids develop good self-esteem, making them feel better about themselves and their work. This positive outlook applies to the students' home cultures as well, demonstrating a demonstrable increase in pride and comfort with their respective cultures. Multicultural education may also improve pupils' ability to interact with others of different backgrounds and ethnicities, resulting in more favorable cross-cultural relationships.

Nature of Multicultural Education

If we talk about the nature of multicultural education, a portion of its elements are as following: i) It comprises of democratic qualities like equity, freedom, fairness, and fraternity; ii) Unity in diversity; iii) Adjustment in the human and materialistic components; iv) Technical and professional education; v) Scientific attitudes in everybody; vi) Consideration of individual difference; vii) Proper performance of abilities; viii) To instill a sense of brotherhood; ix) Transmission of good standards and values of various societies and customs; x) Getting acquainted with different types of civilization and culture; xi) To make a peaceful and stable society without any discrimination; xii) To socialize different cultures among students of different backgrounds.

Need of Multicultural Curriculum

There are many more reasons to implement a Multicultural Curriculum in our classroom. i) A

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Multicultural curriculum exposes students to various cultural values through activities, lectures, discussions, etc.; ii) It allows students to identify cultural as well as physical differences. iii) It also develops a sense of respect amongst classmates; iv) Implementing a Multicultural curriculum at a young age nurtures students to reflect on their cultural diversity with pride; v) It implants patience, liberalism, and individualism in students; vi) It fosters friendships, encourages interaction, and improves communication skills; vii) A multicultural classroom boosts student engagement and improves the attention span; viii) Students who are taught through a Multicultural curriculum tend to have better confidence; ix) A multicultural classroom is hence, more inclusive and positive; x) It also promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills; xi) It enables students to understand the need to accept diversity and eliminate racism and issues based on thnicity or diverse groups for a better future; xii) Eventually a multicultural curriculum produces better thinkers and improves academic performance.

Ways to Improve Multicultural Education in the Classroom

In today's fast-paced world, it's becoming increasingly necessary to promote education programs that meet the demands of a diverse range of students. Here are some of the most effective strategies to implement intercultural education in your classroom. i) Understand Your Students; ii) Identify their Strengths and Weaknesses; iii) Encourage Them to Share Real-Life Experiences; iv) Organize Open Discussions; v) Plan Group Activities; vi) Cultural Food Swap; vii) Encourage Cultural Storytelling; viii) Hold Multicultural Seminars and Events; ix) Schedule a Monthly Culture Day; x) Celebrate Native Festivals.

Four Ways to Implement Multicultural Education

Be Aware of Biases: Challenge the status quo to eliminate bias. Question inequalities that occur within the school or community. **Value Life Experiences:** Give students the opportunity to share life experiences if they feel comfortable as it allows others to either feel validated in their own experience or provides exposure for others to grow and learn from. **Understanding Students Learning Styles:** Students from different backgrounds can learn in different ways. Lessons should be designed to allow all students to succeed. **Assign Multicultural Projects:** Researching different cultural backgrounds is a great way to get students thinking and understanding how others act. Language and the arts are great subjects to incorporate multiculturalism into the classroom.

The Dimensions of Multicultural Education

Multicultural education has five main characteristics and goals. These are a) **Content Integration:** Content integration deals with the extent to which teachers use examples and content from a variety of cultures in their teaching.

Knowledge Construction

Teachers help students to understand, investigate, and determine how the implicit cultural assumptions, frames of reference, perspectives, and biases within a discipline influence the ways in which knowledge is constructed. c) **An Equity Pedagogy:** An equity pedagogy exists when teachers modify their teaching in ways that will facilitate the academic achievement of students from diverse racial, cultural, gender, and social-class groups. d) **Prejudice Reduction:** This dimension focuses on the characteristics of students' racial attitudes and how they can be modified by teaching methods and materials. e) **An Empowering School Culture:** Grouping and labeling practices, sports participation, disproportionality in achievement, and the interaction of the staff and the students across ethnic and racial lines are examined to create a school culture that empowers students from diverse racial, ethnic, and gender groups.

Benefits and Shortcomings of Multicultural Education An Overview

Smith (2009) asserted that success or failure of multicultural education depends on the effective preparation of teachers and administrators. When the teachers and administrators understand the learning needs of students and recognize how these needs can be different than the needs of the students from the dominant culture, then the actual learning occurs. That is, when “we really see, know the students we must teach” (Delpit, 1995, p. 183), we start making a difference in the lives of these students.

The Impact of Multicultural Education on Students

Multicultural education not only enables students to get acquainted with different cultures but also inculcates in students an attitude of respect for the culture of others besides their own culture, sensitivity and empathy towards the culture of others. This allows the students to become more open minded to other cultures and to be more readily accepting of intercultural differences. By engaging in such multicultural dialogue, students are able to effectively communicate with peers from diverse backgrounds and achieve improved results due to a better understanding. Multicultural education has a significant and positive impact on society.

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Different students who have studied in a multicultural environment are more likely to work together in the future.

The Advantages of Multicultural Classroom

There are myriad of benefits of a multicultural classroom for students. Here are a few: i) Exposes students to different cultures; ii) Fosters acceptance and tolerance in a learning environment; iii) Teaches multiple perspectives; iv) Encourages critical thinking; v) Helps to build an international network

Conclusion

This blog tells us about multicultural education and effective teaching strategies that can be used in the classroom. It highly focuses on bringing together students from all backgrounds and promoting collaborative learning. Also, helps teachers interact with students from different cultures that accelerate the professional growth of a teacher. So, in a rapidly changing world, it is important to promote a multicultural education program that caters to the needs of diversified students. More research must be done to assess the direct impact of multicultural education on the benefits I've discussed herein. Research must be done to evaluate the longitudinal effects of a multicultural education. Also, research should compare the effects of multicultural education on members of the dominant group and members of marginalized groups.

References

- [1] Donna M. Gollnick, Philip C. Chinn, *Multicultural Education in a Pluralistic Society*, California State University, Los Angeles, 2006.
- [2] James A. Banks, *The Routledge International Companion to Multicultural Education*, New York and London, 2009.
- [3] Carl A. Grant, Joy L. Lei, *Global Constructions of Multicultural Education*, New York, 2001.
- [4] Osman Ozturgul, *Current Issues in Education, USA*, 2011.
- [5] Shailja Gupta, *Multicultural Education: A Holistic Approach towards Development of Globalized Society*, Allahabad, India, 2022.
- [6] Johan Dwi Saputro; Mukhamad Murdiono, *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, Yogyakarta State University, Indonesia, 2020.
- [7] Farideh Salili, Rumjahn Hoosain, *Multicultural Education: Issues, Policies and Practices*, Hong Kong, 2001.
- [8] Fatih Yilmaz, *Multiculturalism and Multicultural education: A Case Study of Teacher Candidates Perceptions*, Turkey, 2016.
- [9] Sonia Nieto, *Multicultural Education Review*, University of Massachusetts Amherst, MA, USA, 2017.

EXPLORING THE IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY SYSTEM IN STUDENTS' SAFETY MEASURES AND TECHNOLOGY USAGE AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract

Information and Communication Technologies have rapidly prevailed among children. Personal technologies facilitating the students to gain some learning experiences both in and out of the schools also include many threats. It is important for students to have a high awareness of safe internet and computer use to overcome these threats. Whatever may be, family members should help their children to be not cheated by development of technology and to help to develop their technological knowledge. The main objective of this study is to investigate the importance of family system in students' safety measures and technology usage among higher secondary students. The study was conducted in Tenkasi of Tamilnadu with a sample size of 148 higher secondary students, using simple random sampling technique. The findings of the study showed that a positive correlation between students' safety measures and technology usage among higher secondary school students.

Key word: *Family system, Safety, Technology, Higher secondary*

Introduction

Education is one of the most important factors of everyday life, so that, education is determination of a part of our lifestyle, and including digital education has become more important contrary to traditional education in the contemporary society. Traditional lifestyle has changed over time to modern lifestyle, though men still play an instrumental role in the family, women have shifted from an expressive role to a more instrumental one. The economic system has facilitated this freeing of women from household chores and their entrance to the labour market (Madani & Qureshi, n.d.). Therefore, women's share of the labour force has increased in almost all the countries. Along with this the family structure has changed over time, where more Indian's are moving into nuclear households. Hence, the world has seen an emergence of dual earner nuclear families. The world, has not just witnessed a change in family structure, but also the rapid proliferation of information and communication technology, is an unstoppable force, touching virtually every sphere of modern life and childhood is no exception. With close to billion users worldwide, the Internet has become a key public infrastructure that has the potential to connect students (Alahdadi & Razaghi, 2018). While bringing many benefits to the society and being conducive to innovation, students' learning and development, the fast paced technological innovation and increasing accessibility of ICTs also provide new pathways to sexual abuse and exploitation of students.

Student Safety Measures

The internet as a new medium offers unlimited opportunities for learning and knowledge sharing but it can also shape specific inappropriate attitudes and cultivate erroneous and potentially dangerous ideas. As the number of young people who go online worldwide increases' so it needs the concern about the safeness of the websites they visit. For instance, there are more than thirteen millions of students online in Europe. Approximately thirty per cent (four million) of these children are under twelve years old and the rest seventy per cent (nine million) are between twelve and seventeen year old. Similar statistics apply to the other continents as well. Based on the fact that the intentions of several sites are to deceive their users or to promote unsafe content and ideas (e.g. porn, terrorism, and drugs)and given the large number of online students, initiatives like safer internet are not only justifiable but they are considered as vital. Accordingly Lazarinis (2010), the World Wide Web has rapidly become one of the most widely used services of the internet along with e- mail. Its friendly interface and its hypermedia features attract a significant number of users around the globe. As a result, the web has become a pool of various types of data, dispensed in a measureless number of locations. Users of different cultural backgrounds, different interests and diversified aims visit daily various web locations either in their natural language or most often in English. At the same time, online risks connect directly or indirectly affect physically or mentally. These risks are synthesized based on the online sites safer internet surfing for children and adolescents.

Objectives

This paper focuses on the following objectives along with these hypotheses

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- 1) To test any significant difference in students' safety measures and technology usage with respect to parent education, type of family.
- 2) To observe the relationship between students' safety measures and technology usage among the students.

Hypotheses

- 1) There is no significant difference in the students' safety measures with respect to parent education.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the students' safety measures with respect to type of family.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the technology usages with respect to parent education.
- 4) There is no significant difference in the technology usages with respect to type of family.
- 5) There is no statistically significant correlation between students' safety measures and technology usage of students.

Research Method

Descriptive survey method has been employed in this study. Tools used for the study:

The following tool has been used to collect data for the present study. The Scale for students' safety measures and technology usage were developed by the Researcher with the guidance of the Research Supervisor. Selection of the sample: The sample for the study was selected randomly. The sample consisted of 148 higher secondary students at Tenkasi district in Tamil Nadu. Statistical techniques: The relation between students' safety measures and technology usage were revealed through independent samples t-test with respect to parent education, type of family. In addition, the Pearson's product movement correlation was used to find the relationship between students' safety measures and technology usage. Data collection tool: Data collection tools of this study were the students' safety measures and technology usage scale and a questionnaire prepared in order to obtain the demographic features of students. There are 15 items in the scale prepared to determine basic factors about participant Students' Safe and 13 items Technology Usage. A Likert-type scale was used in order to measure students' agreement levels as; 1= 'Strongly Disagree', 2 = 'Disagree', 3 = 'Neutral', 4 = 'Agree', and 5 = 'Strongly agree' for Student Safety Measures questionnaire and 1= 'Never', 2 = 'Some times', 3 = 'Always' for Student Technology Usage.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the students' safety measures with respect to parent education

Table 1 Difference in students' safety measures with respect to parent education

Variables	Category	N	Mean	S.D	'P' value and significant level
Parent Education	School Education	85	56.13	5.23	P = 0.471
	Higher Education	63	56.52	4.72	P > 0.05
					NS

From the above table, the 'P' value is 0.471 which is greater than the 'P' value (0.05) at 95% level of confidence and the hypothesis assumed that there is no significant difference in students' safety measures due to parent education is statistically not significant. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference in students' safety measures owing to parent education among the higher secondary students.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the students' safety measures with respect to type of family

Table 2 Difference in students' safety measures with respect to type of family

Variables	Category	N	Mean	S.D	'P' value and significant level
Type of Family	Joint Family	38	56.92	5.19	P = 0.887
	Nuclear Family	110	56.08	4.97	P > 0.05 NS

From the above table, the 'P' value is 0.887 which is greater than the 'P' value (0.05) at 95% level of confidence and the hypothesis assumed that there is no significant difference in students' safety measures due to type of family is statistically not significant. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference in

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students' safety measures owing to type of family among the higher secondary students.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the technology usages with respect to parent education

Table 3 Difference in technology usages with respect to parent education

Variables	Category	N	Mean	S.D	'P' value and significant level
Parent Education	School Education	58	31.36	1.75	P = 1.101 P > 0.05
	Higher Education	63	31.51	2.02	NS

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the technology usages with respect to type of family

Table 4 Difference in technology usages with respect to type of family

Variables	Category	N	Mean	S.D	'P' value and significant level
Type of Family	Joint Family	38	31.76	2.24	P = 1.735 P > 0.05
	Nuclear Family	110	31.75	1.71	NS

From the above table, the 'P' value is 1.735 which is greater than the 'P' value (0.05) at 95% level of confidence and the hypothesis assumed that there is no significant difference in technology usages due to type of family is statistically not significant. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference in technology usages owing to type of family among the higher secondary students.

Hypothesis 5: There is no statistically significant correlation between students' safety measures and technology usage of students

Table 5 Relationship between students' safety measures and technology usage of students

Variable	No	Correlation 'r'	Remark
Students' safety measures	148	0.072	Significant at 0.05 level
Technology usage	148		

The Pearson's Product moment correlation test has been employed to find out the relationship between students' safety measures and technology usage among higher secondary school students. As the calculated 'r' value is 0.072 that the hypothesis "There is no significant relationship between students' safety measures and technology usage among higher secondary school students" is rejected. According to the interpretation of coefficient of correlation table, the calculated correlation value (0.072) is between (+.001 to +.10) category. So, it is inferred that there is significant positive correlation between students' safety measures and technology usage among higher secondary school students.

Discussion

Students' safety measures are followed at school and home. The majority of the students mentioned that they discussed internet dangers with their parents and made efforts to monitor their internet use and access by setting restrictions and limitations at home. Some of the students claimed that their parents were trying to protect by frightening them about the internet and forbidding using certain programs such as Facebook, Micro Soft Network (MSN) etc. Specifically, even if joint family members applied safety systems several weaknesses were revealed since some of the students mentioned that they were exposed to inappropriate material (i.e. sexual content). It is notable to mention that some students reported that they managed to violate or break school security codes. Students of nuclear families are using Educational technology for education, fun, entertainment and socializing and use beneficial to students in various ways. Generally, Students use

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technology to their knowledge in areas like wording, spelling, grammar and learning new words, and improve their arithmetical, numeracy and mathematical skills. The educational technology also allows students to gather information for school projects. This is done mainly by using the various search engines such as google, yahoo, ask-jeeves, altavista and others. Students may have access to literature, music and movies through established virtual and online libraries and obtain various kinds of information. According to Suparyanto dan Rosad (2015, 2020), the internet provides students with the opportunity to communicate with people from all around the world mainly using chat rooms such as MIRC, Skype, MSN and various forums on websites. Using the above, they meet and get in touch with people from different places and keep in contact with people, e.g. classmates that have now gone abroad and relatives/friends that are far away from home.

Conclusion

In India, the family system is an identity that is joint and nuclear. Moreover, students and teachers presuppose that type of family is a particular culture in society. Two types of family have the identity of personal attitudes because, with that identity, they interact and influence one another, including interactions between their children (Society, 2022). For the development of the globalized society, family system, and parental education must be valued in the education from primary level to a higher level so that the entire global society can move ahead on the path of progress by rising above the discrimination of the country.

References

- [1] Alahdadi, N., & Razaghi, M. (2018). Investigation of lifestyle and identity Changes of Khorramabad Residents in Iran. 2(1), 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.22034/jhi.2018.62709>
- [2] Lazarinis, F. (2010). Online risks obstructing safe internet access for students. *Electronic Library*, 28(1), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02640471011023441>
- [3] Madani, M., & Qureshi, N. (n.d.). Impact of Media on the Modern Lifestyle of Women in Karachi. 33–49.
- [4] Society, G. (2022). Multicultural Education : A Holistic Approach towards Development of Multicultural Education : A Holistic Approach towards Development of Globalized Society Shailja Gupta. July. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20329.77925>

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Introduction

Education is a lifelong process. It enlightens every individual 'knowledge and help them to make their ways better. Education also helps to transform one's behaviour. The future of a nation is designed inside the classroom. Classroom is a heterogeneous environment, where learners thought process not only differs, but also their ethnicity, their language and also their culture. Also, like Character, everyone has various cultural and linguistic background because of globalization the world has become smaller. probably, the global citizens are having education anywhere around the world. Schools are the component of society. And it's one of the building block and basic unit of society. Today's schools are more diverse in culture and language. So, it's the prime responsibility of the teachers to be known about their student's background for better understanding and effective teaching. It's the responsibility of teachers to bind the minds of young generation together.

Cross Cultural Education

The term Cross cultural education also is often used interchangeably with inter cultural education. A definition of cross-cultural education is that it involves a mixture of culture in which a student is made aware of his or her own another that comprises of his or her own education. This allows the learners to understand their culture, norms traditions, beliefs and also to celebrate them. It allows the learners to respect their culture and also respect would be sensitive towards their own culture and also would learn to respect the cultural differences and will not discriminate any one based on their culture.

The Teacher

Teachers demands and expectations are more Today's teachers always play a supporting role inside classrooms. They have to play the role of mentor, manager, trainers and guide-Classroom are the miniature of cross-cultural society. It's the need of the hour that teachers are to be flexible and to friendly. Classroom teachers are to be prepared, to teach and interact with learners from different cultural background. But classrooms are place what's done inside the four walls will impact the learners lifelong. To face this challenge and accomplish, teachers should be good communicators and chameleons for understanding the learner's culture.

Schools & Cultural Settings

It's important that teacher should be more professional and dedicated to understand the multi-cultural setting inside the schools-classrooms are the basic unit of schools, schools are basic unit of society. So, what are the measures to be taken in the society have to be implemented inside the schools. So, there should be a positive wave throughout the school. For an effective cross – cultural communication, among students from multiple and various cultures, the schools have to able to understand the learners as well as, teacher's beliefs, traditions myths about their culture. Being humane is one of the basic practices to have an effective cross-cultural communication & to have effective teaching process. Cultural concepts are to be supported in a school setting. Culture is unique and specific for each community-When people come together it's needed to inter wine by a single thread of humanity and communication schools should act as a co-operative community to promote mutual understanding and have for knowledge.

Role of Teacher

Teacher's aim in the classroom is to create equal participation against all distinction in the form of race ethnic, social class and culture. Teachers are responsible for transforming the learners to have a holistic view about education. Teachers have responsibility to develop moral understanding, effective communication. Teacher bids these various groups by evoking the common factor friendship through her effective communication. Teacher trains the learners from various places to be socially aware by providing valuable and trustworthy educational experience. To develop a trustworthy relationship, humanity good understanding among learners and teachers should act like a coordinator, a guide and facilitator the teacher's approach should have.

- 1) Contribution Approach
- 2) Transformational Approach

Contribution Approach

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The teacher should know well and good about the learner's cultural backgrounds she/he must have a clear understanding of the festivals, ethnic heroes specifically.

Transformational Approach

The Teacher should know in depth of the cultural practices, followed by the various learners. The important social, political and economic actions which transformed. The specific culture to admirable one.

Qualities of Good Teacher

- 1) Maintenance of Good Relation
- 2) Prejudices
- 3) Respect to every culture
- 4) Accepting every teacher
- 5) Equity Pedagogy

Respect to Every Culture

Learners would be from Various Culture, ethnic beliefs, Community backgrounds etc. Teachers should respect every learner belief, Customs and have good respect about their beliefs. Teachers should be generous and lovable. They must also treat every learner equally without bias.

Acceptance

The teachers should be broad minded. She\He must not view each learner's culture and their beliefs in his\her own idea. Teachers should have divergent thinking and have to be polite with everyone. He\She should not be irritated or frustrated. Teacher should not consider their beliefs as wild joke.

Reduction of Prejudice

The teachers should prejudice because of the knowledge gained. Knowledge is power. The teachers with the help of the content knowledge should be able to construct the knowledge of learn. She\He can take steps to spread the seeds of lore among young generations in to ad of enveloping hatred among themselves. They have to spend their knowledge in knowing about the customs, beliefs traditions cultures. Be the model of leathers.

Maintenance of Good Relation

To develop on strong relationship with learners, the teachers should be more lovable and stronger enough in her\his mind to accept the changes in the society. He\She be tolerant towards the belief of the young minds. They should imitate like the learner to knows in deep about their culture. He\She should not judge him\her radically or rationally.

Culturally Responsive Teaching

- 1) Adopt the inclusive curriculums that reflects the diversity of society.
- 2) Have prior knowledge, including their culture a language.
- 3) Cultural sensitivity.
- 4) Positive Perspectives on parents and families of culturally & linguistically diverse student.

An effective teacher accepts the diverse culture among learners and accept learners from different cultures as human beings. In particularly respecting the ethnic minorities and making them to feel safe. Teachers are in the best position to understand & recognize that students have diverse cultural backgrounds and can adopt their instruction to meet these diverse learning needs.

Conclusion

Thus, an effective teacher has good cross-Cultural Communication with learners by their good language skill and ability. A teacher by acting as a good Cross-Cultural Communicator sow the seeds of humanity, lore, brother hood equality, tolerance among learners. There be building a global citizenship and making learners as global citizens and more humans.

References

- [1] <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/profcommsontario/chapter/cross-cultural-communication/>
- [2] <https://www.northeastern.edu/graduate/blog/cross-cultural-communication/>
- [3] <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000261998.locale=en>

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THE PORTRAYAL OF FEMININITY AND EMPOWERMENT IN THEWORKS OF

INDIAN AUTHORS

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Abstract

Writing has witnessed the roles of women growing through ages, but until recent times, most of the writers were men and the portrayal of women in literature was without doubt biased. The origin of Indian writing in English was sown during the period of the British rule in India. Now the seed has blossomed into an ever green tree, aromatic flowers and ripe fruits. The fruits are being tasted not only by the indigenous people, but they are also being chewed and digested by the foreigners. It happened only after the constant caring, pruning and feeding. Gardeners' like Sri Aurobindo, Tagore, R.K. Narayan, Chetan Bhagat, Raja Rao-to name only a few, looked after the fond plant day and night were the notable writers. Their novels have women characters not as vital characters but are often minor characters like friends, sisters, mother, wife or foreigners. They portray feminine characters who accept marriage as their destiny, about which they can do nothing but suffer tolerantly. The writings were explorers to the current, Indian women's roles and portrayal in literature is a sign of the changes occurring historically for women. The insignificance and coercion of women prior to the mid of 19th century is connected by the small roles of females in literature. As women gained equality, the leading actress continued to transform. By studying these changes, it is observed that not only do the characters symbolize the female identity, but also the leading actress transforms into the new figures that women aspire to be. These writings were grew their potential and not only enhance a women's world as writers, entrepreneurs, mystics, painters, counselors, scientists but can also provide a better vision to the men's world.

Keywords: Indian women, feminine, English, portrayal, literature, equality, potential, writers.

Introduction

Writing has witnessed the roles of women growing through ages, but until recent era, most of the published authors were men and the portrayal of women in literature was without doubt biased. However, the contribution of women to oral folklore cannot be taken for granted-in folk songs, stories, poetry and literature in general. Here's a look at how women were portrayed in literature through eras. Indian Writing in English is not a recent genre. It is as old as British, American, African and Common Wealth Writings in English. The depiction of Characters, Women characters in particular, differs from Country to country. However portrayal of male dominance over women is a common feature in all these writings including Indian writing in English.

The portrayal of images of women by Indian novelists like Bankim Chandra Chatterjee, Devi Chaudhurani, Torudutt, Anand, Narayan, Raja Rao, Bhabani Bhattacharya, Manohar Malgonkar, Kamala Markendeya, Ruth Praver Jhabvala, Anita Desi, Nayanatara Tara Sahgal, Shoba dey, Arundhati Roy, Vikram Seth, Chetan Bhagath, is not uniform. It differs from novel to novel and writer to writer. The research scholar seeks to investigate that there is a vast difference between the portrayal of images of women and the real conditions in which women are forced to live. In reality they continue to live in awful conditions of subjugation, desperate dependence and above all denial of domestic, social and economic freedom by men. Mulk Raj Anand's presentation of images of women can be considered more realistic than those depicted by other writers like Narayan and Raja Rao. The image of Sohini, Bakra's sister, in Untouchable is woefully so pathetic that she is the symbol of oppression.

In Coolie two women characters Gujri and Biwi Uttamkour are exposed exploiting Munoo, the hero. Parbati, a pathetic character in the novel, is kind hearted and religious and she shows kindness and affection to Munoo, but she weeps when her husband is taken away to the police station. In Two Leaves and a Bud Anand depicts the pathetic state of women characters under the colonial exploitation Sajani, Gangu, the hero's wife, who represents the fastidious village women whose whole life had been spent cleaning and washing and cooking and cleaning again looks after her husband, Gangu, but she herself gets infected with malaria and dies.

R.K.Narayan was one among the greatest Indian novelists. Most of his novels were on contemporary social issues. His novels have women characters not as central characters but are often secondary characters like mother, sister, friends, wife or foreigners. Susila, Rosie, Rukmini, Laxmi, etc. are his different female characters in different novels, but they are not protesting women. These characters of women have the usual feminine weakness and surrender themselves under the male domination.

He portrays female characters who accept marriage as their fate, about which they can do nothing but suffer patiently. These characters are ever shy and demure as traditional Indian women should always be.

Contemporary popular fiction Indian writers like Chetan Bhagat and Anita Nair have showcased the

new woman in their works. Chetan Bhagat's writing is more feminine than masculine. He gives voice and shows his concerns more to his ladies than to his heroes. Bhagat added recording of his concern for women characters tells us the fact that steps towards women empowerment can be seen to be speeding. Bhagat claims women empowerment as one of the confident effects of globalization; at the same time, it is incontrovertible that his novels definitely give us cultural shocks which are an expected shock of globalization, modernization, and commercial exploitation. These changes represent the pathetic cry of a majority of orthodox Hindu women in Indian society, thus, it is understood that being under the guise of liberation, there is a definite degeneration in the status of women as voiced forth in the novels of Chetan.

In *The Three Mistakes of My Life*, his heroine Vidya is so worried to lose her virginity that she chooses to do it right on her birthday. Moreover, she chooses her tutor and her brother's best friend Govind for that reason. She is younger, but bolder than all other lady characters of the novelist. Govind is a rational man he understands that it is wrong, but Vidya doesn't let him think anything at all. She is a nice-looking little seductress. Govind regrets his deeds after finishing the course, but Vidya is happy afar expectations to the opposite. She thanks God for making her adult and feels happy after losing her virginity. She speaks; Wow, I am an adult now and am no longer a virgin, so cool. Thank God⁴ (Bhagat: 2008, 20)

While Chetan portrays his women characters as harbingers of social change and equality, an aspect which is evident in his book *One Night @ the Call Centre*, where men and women are treated equally and work in night shifts. Nair's characters have their own pain and sorrow but they overcome their entire struggle, a fact you'll notice especially in her bestseller, *Ladies Coupe*. Nair feels nothing has changed in the terms of mentality, "That a woman could live a fulfilled life on her own terms was a concept writers seemed unable to conceive or unwilling to explore. Sadly, very little has changed. Women in fiction may have shrugged some of the strait jacketed representations but anytime a woman character chooses to live life on her terms, readers tend to get agitated. Hence, Chetan Bhagat has skillfully portrayed the element of vitality in his women central characters. His woman characters believe in an absolute, a perfect, a pure and a noble freedom. They always take inventiveness in the courtship. Thus, they break the social etiquette – man ever chases woman. They are the chasers and the men are the chased. Bhagat is the first novelist amongst his contemporaries who has delineated woman as the hunter and the man as the excavation under her blind passion to suit his purpose. His women use all diplomacy to serve the female instinct.

According to author Anita Nair, "Literature has always been ambivalent in its representation of women. Good women as in ones who accepted societal norms were rewarded with happily ever after". Raja Rao always portrays women keeping in mind the scriptures of *Manu Smriti*, which shows the duties and behaviour of women. A submissive attitude is one of the striking features on Raja Rao's characterisation. His ideal women- Savithri, Shantaha and Jayalakshmi are submissive ones. In *Kanthapura*, not at all assertive but fully obedient wife to her husband is highlighted.

Conclusion

Those constructions of studies, the readers acknowledged the work of women portrayed by Indian writers as a strong way to spread modernism and feminist statements. In the past 20 years, there has been a remarkable progress when we talk about feminist pictures in writings in the Indian literature. In today's generation, women are portrayed more by writers. Novels written by modern women writers focus on the issues related to women, for instance; rape and other societal issues as well, like corruption and injustice. Most of the stories focus on the themes of unknown psyche of females, and we can witness many such stories where the sorrows of an unlucky housewife are portrayed. These novels are much appreciated by the readers to explore the women.

References

- [1] Bareilly: Prakash Book Depot. Print. Uppal, Ruchi- Bajaj, Sheetal. Predicament of Indian Women in the work of Mulk Raj Anand. IJEAR. Print, 1974, 2012, 4.
- [2] Bhagat Chetan, *One Night @ The Call Centre*. Delhi: Rupa Co. 2005: p. 104. .Print.
- [3] Bhagat Chetan, *The 3 Mistakes of My Life*. Delhi: Rupa Co., 2008: 20. .Print.
- [4] Mishra, Ravi Kumar. Representation of modern culture and modern trend in Chetan Bhagat

DOMAINS FOR HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT OF AN INDIVIDUAL'S LEARNING

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Introduction

“Learning is a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning” - **Ambrose , 2010**

Learning is not something done to students, but rather something students themselves do. It is the direct result of how students interpret and respond to their experiences. The change in the learner may happen at the level of knowledge, attitude or behavior. As a result of learning, learners come to see concepts, ideas, and/or the world differently. The student is viewed Holistically through Seven Domains: spiritual, mental, social, emotional, creative, natural, and physical. Simply put, holistic development is the social, emotional, physical, mental, and intellectual growth of a person.

Domains

According to the Blooms Taxonomy, Domains are divided into three. They are,

1. Cognitive Domain

The cognitive domain contains learning skills predominantly related to mental (thinking) processes. The cognitive process includes thinking, intelligence and language skills. Learning processes in the cognitive domain include a hierarchy of skills involving processing information, constructing understanding, applying knowledge, solving problems, and conducting research. There are six levels of cognitive complexity: knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation.

2. Affective Domain

Most people think of learning as an intellectual or mental function. However, learning is not a just a cognitive (mental) function. You can also learn attitudes, behaviors, and physical skills. The affective domain involves our feelings, emotions and attitudes. The affective domain involves our feelings, emotions, and attitudes. This domain includes the manner in which we deal with things emotionally, such as feelings, values, appreciation, enthusiasms, motivations, and attitudes. This domain is categorized into 5 sub-domains, which include: (1). Receiving (2) Responding (3) Valuing (4) Organization (5) Characterization

3. Psychomotor Domain

Psychomotor objectives are those specific to discreet physical functions, reflex actions and interpretive movements. It is interesting to note that while the cognitive taxonomy was described in 1956, and the affective in 1964, the psychomotor domain were not fully described until the 1970s. Traditionally, these types of objectives are concerned with the physically encoding of information, with movement and/or with activities where the gross and fine muscles are used for expressing or interpreting information or concepts. This area also refers to natural, autonomic responses or reflexes. The psychomotor domain is comprised of utilizing motor skills and coordinating them.

Domains Role in Holistic Development

An individual can accept that all three domains are very important for holistic development. Researchers were proved that all three domains are inter-related. Now it's the time for us to know that the development will happen while we are giving emphasis to particular domain at particular period. Instructions should be done to students through the domains, where we have to give more importance to one or two domains, rather than on all three at a stretch. For instance, we can give more emphasis on affective and psychomotor domain during the primary stage. During the primary stage, if we are training an individual with valued based education and practicing it through activities, which results in positive behavioural change. During the middle stage, we need to give more emphasis on Cognition and Psychomotor domain. After Adolescent period, we need to give more and equal emphasis to all three domains. If we follow this strategy while we instructing an individual for development, surely it results in Holistic Development in Learning and constructing knowledge.

Conclusion

To put in a nut shell, all three domains plays a vital role in the holistic development. But we have to choose and give emphasis on particular domains according to the stages of an individual. It will result in construction of knowledge through thinking, feeling and activities.

References

- [1] https://www.google.com/search?q=Bloom%27s+of+Taxonomy&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwiRooyHstb8AhX0cGwGHaxvDlkQ_AUoAXoECAIQAw&biw=1024&bih=612&dpr=1#imgrc=2Bre1TBGoG6X5M

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HOLISTIC LEARNING

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Abstract

Holistic learning focuses on an individual's potential holistic development and teaches students how to develop the aspects a person needs to live a better life. helps both children and adults think creatively and find solutions to any situation where physical activity can greatly benefit. Regular participation in physical activity ultimately leads to physical, mental, social, emotional and ethical development. Since an individual's life largely depends on the age and adulthood of a child, physical activity is an excellent way to develop these areas and live life in a great way.

Introduction

“Holistic education focuses on the possible development of people, to enable individuals to be and be the best they can be and experience it all they can get away from life and achieve their Goals.” (Marshman,2010). Holistic education aims to meet the student's emotional, social, ethical or moral, and academic needs in an integrated learning format by addressing their emotional, social, and ethical needs. There is a strong focus on providing students with academic and nonacademic needs in a positive school environment. Teachers have the best chance to use holistic teaching strategies to support students in finding their identities and the significance of connections to their communities and their wider world. Many schools in India include holistic objectives to improve the educational system. While a single overall principle informs holistic education, teachers may use various techniques to foster a holistic learning culture. The question is how physical education and sports can contribute to the holistic learning process. The definition of physical education itself states that physical education is the development of general aspects of health. This includes holistic learning helps in physical, mental, emotional, social, ethical and spiritual aspects. All major areas of development – physical and motor development, social and emotional development, language development, cognitive and ethical development, creativity and curiosity is developed through physical activity and sports.

Physical Fitness of the Student

Fitness is the ability to manage illness, fatigue, stress and reduce sedentary behavior while performing daily activities with optimal performance, endurance and strength. Staying fit is an essential part of leading a healthy lifestyle. Brain health is important throughout life because the brain is involved in both mental processes and physical activities in the human body. In adults, brain health is disease-free, represents optimal structure and function, and is measured by quality of life and ability to function effectively in everyday life. A child's brain health can be measured in relation to the development of attention, task behavior, memory, and academic performance in educational settings. (Campbell et al., 2013) This chapter provides an overview of recent research findings on the contribution of physical activity to cognitive function and brain health in children and the attainment of health-enhancing levels of physical fitness. For this reason, physical education is a core subject in the curricula of major universities around the world. Studies have shown that incorporating fitness activities into your schedule not only improves cardiovascular health, but also helps with muscle strength development, leading to a healthy lifestyle. Physical fitness has multiple components and is conceptualized as related to performance or health. Performance-related fitness peculiarity regarding individual exercise capacity are most commonly associated with individual exercise performance. Conversely, health-related fitness is generalized to health conditions and can be positively or negatively influenced by physical activity habits. (Haskell, 2006)

Social Well-Being of Students

Social well-being can be defined as sharing, developing and maintaining meaningful relationships with others. This helps you feel authentic and valuable, and gives you a sense of connection and belonging (What Is Social Well-Being? Definition, Types, and How to Achieve It, n.d.). Happiness improves academic performance, behavior, social integration and student satisfaction. Wellbeing improves teachers' ability to interact with students, convey concepts, face challenges, and avoid burnout. Feeling recognized for who you are is an integral part of emotional and social well-being. Feeling left out is harmful or contrary to self-respect and dignity. Students who are seen as peers and feel they have the same opportunities to achieve as others are more likely to fulfill their academic potential and admire the school for its friendly and welcoming atmosphere. In fact, they are more acceptable to different people. Student social well-being has been described

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as the degree to which they feel included and integrated in their social and academic environment (Kern et al. 2015).

Ethical or Moral Development

Moral development refers to the process by which people develop a progressive sense of what is right and wrong, right and wrong. As the term development suggests, human moral feeling is generally viewed as a transition from simple, restrictive definitions of good and evil to more complex ways of distinguishing between good and evil. (Ethical Development & Maturity, 2019) Ethical development, also known as moral development, focuses on the formation, transformation, and understanding of morality from childhood through adulthood. Morality is developed throughout life. An individual's experiences influence his or her ethical development and behavior on moral issues.

Academic Development

Students who become overly emotional or have difficulty concentrating. When students are unable to concentrate on their tasks or become overly emotional, they are unable to process information and learn. These are potential factors that can affect a student's academic development. As children learn, they begin to build on future successes. Ultimately, all that learning is incorporated into careers that help the now-grown person provide for his family. (Study.com | Take Online Courses. Earn College Credit. Research Schools, Degrees & Careers, n.d.) In addition, communities are influenced by all the knowledge gained and the achievements individuals make to society through their careers. receive. In some cases, skills extend beyond careers into public and community service.

Conclusion

It has therefore been concluded that physical activity, when properly planned to focus on a given aspect, can aid in the process of holistic learning in children. Games can perform that task. But the problem lies in the planning and execution of game situations, giving you the opportunity to explore and create rather than being confined to rules and repetitious activities.

References

- [1] What Is Social Well-Being? Definition, Types, and How to Achieve It. (n.d). <https://www.betterup.com/blog/what-is-social-well-being-definition-types-and-how-to-achieve-it>
- [2] Ethical Development & Maturity. (2019, July 10). Business Ethics Resource Center. <https://www.businessethicsresourcecenter.org/ethical-decision-making/ethical->

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A STUDY ON ALTRUISM AS AN OUTCOME OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Multicultural education is teaching people who are from different cultured backgrounds. When people from different cultured gather and do schooling in one place, it is a better opportunity for them to accept, and adapt to new cultures, mindsets, moral directions, beliefs, etc. The purpose of the study was to assess the level of altruism based on demographic variables among multicultural educated students. The results indicated that a significant difference between and among groups was seen based on age, gender, location education, family type, socioeconomic status and birth order in the level of altruism. There has been an evidence of a significant relationship between education and altruism was found.

Keywords: *Altruism, Multicultural education.*

Introduction

Multicultural Education

Any form of training or teaching that incorporates the history, literary works, moral principles, and worldviews of people from many cultural backgrounds is referred to "multicultural education". Teachers may, for instance, modify or combine classroom lessons to better reflect the cultural diversity of the students in a particular class. The term "culture" is frequently used to refer to a wide range of factors, including colour, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, and "exceptionality," a label given to kids who have particular needs or difficulties. To remove obstacles to educational opportunities and achievement for students from various cultural backgrounds, multicultural education is founded on the idea that all kids, regardless of culture, deserve an equal education. To teach culturally diverse students effectively, educational strategies that value and acknowledge their cultural backgrounds are necessary. This is because multicultural education assumes that students' learning and thinking processes are profoundly influenced by their cultural identity and heritage.

Prosocial Behavior

Positive social interactions and the promotion of social adjustment depend on prosocial activity, a significant moral behaviour (Fabes et al., 1999). Prosocial behaviour, which includes assisting, collaborating, consoling, sharing, and giving, was described as an activity that benefits others (Eisenberg, 1982). A social action that "benefits other individuals or society as a whole" is known as prosocial behaviour, or purpose to benefit others. Examples include assisting, sharing, giving, cooperating, and volunteering. Prosocial behaviours also include following the law and engaging in socially acceptable. These behaviours may be driven by empathy, concern for the welfare and rights of others, as well as egoistic or pragmatic considerations like one's reputation or social standing, the expectation of direct or indirect reciprocity, or adherence to one's system of justice.

Altruism –A prosocial Behaviour

Altruism is a moral concept and ethical behaviour that promotes both a material and quality of life by caring for the welfare and/or happiness of other people or animals. Auguste Comte, a French philosopher, popularised and may have even created the term "altruism" to serve as an antithesis to egoism. The Latin word *alteri*, which means "other people" or "someone else," was the source of the Italian word *altrui*, which he used to create the word. Altruism is defined as the act of doing something for the benefit of another person without expecting anything in return, according to biological studies of field populations of contemporary creatures in return or payment for it. In the therapeutic environment, Steinberg offers the following definition of altruism: "Intentional and voluntary activities that attempt to promote the wellbeing of another person without any external quid pro quo incentives." It is possible to discern between loyalty and concern for the general welfare and altruism. Altruism does not take relationships into account, whereas the latter is based on social ties. If "genuine" altruism is feasible in human psychology, there is a lot of disagreement. According to the psychological egoism idea, act of giving, assisting, or sacrificing can be seen to be fully selfless because the performer may experience some type of intrinsic gain. If intrinsic rewards are considered "benefits," then this argument is acceptable. An ethical theory that holds that people have a moral obligation to help others is also

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sometimes referred to as altruism. In this context, it is frequently contrasted with egoism, the idea that people have a moral duty to put their interests first. The best ways to help others may be found by using logic and evidence, which is meant by effective altruism.

Theoretical background of developing altruism

Psychological altruism is described as "a motivating condition to promote another's well-being" in the International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences. The desire to improve one's well-being is the focus of psychological egoism, which is opposed to psychological altruism. According to the social exchange hypothesis, altruism can only exist when self-benefits outweigh self-costs. The social exchange hypothesis is contested by psychologist Daniel Batson, who looked into this issue. He distinguished four main motives: egoism, altruism, collectivism, and upholding moral principles. According to the empathy-altruism theory, the desire to relieve someone else's suffering causes psychological altruism to exist. Empathic concern is opposed to personal anguish, which drives people to lessen their own negative emotions and boost their good ones by lending a helping hand to someone in need. Empathy is therefore not selfless since altruism serves as a means of avoiding bad sensations and experiencing happy feelings when others ask for aid, or it serves as a means of incentivizing the attainment of social reward or the avoidance of social punishment by assisting. People with empathy care about others' suffering even when it may be prevented, but those without empathy avoid assisting unless it is difficult or impossible to avoid being exposed to another person's suffering.

Objectives

- 1) To investigate the significant difference based on demographic variables.
- 2) To assess the significant relationship between education and altruism.

Hypothesis

- 1) There will be no significant difference based on age, gender, location, education and family type in the level of altruism.
- 2) There will be no significant difference based on Socioeconomic status and birth order in the level of altruism.
- 3) There will be no significant relationship between education and altruism.

Method & Material

The study aimed to analyze the altruism of multiculturalized educated students. The study area is Tirunelveli district, Tamilnadu, India. The data was gathered using a simple random sampling method. Sample size $N = 100$ was taken for this survey. The age limit for the study was from 13 to 18 which has been divided into two groups for analysis. Group one was from 13 to 15 years old and group two was from 16 to 18 years old. Participants were both male ($n = 50$) and female ($n = 50$) taken equally. The participants were distributed based on location as rural and urban. Based on their socioeconomic status the participants were distributed into three groups namely Low, middle and high socioeconomic status. Based on education, the distribution was into two. From 8th std to 10th std one group and 11th std and 12th std were another group. Based on the family, the distribution was made into two, nuclear family and joint family. Based on the birth order of the participants the distribution was made into three the first child, the second child and the third child. The dependent variable of the study is altruism and the independent variable is multicultural education.

Material

The self-reported altruism scale (SRA) can be easily administered, in a self-reported format. The self-reported altruism scale (SRA) is a 5-point Likert-type scale that was developed to evaluate the level of altruism. The scale consists of 20 statements and the respondents are instructed to rate the frequency with which they have engaged in altruistic behaviours. The results of the scale concluded with higher scores 'greater the level of altruism'. The responses are through numbers from 1 to 5 representing 'never-1', 'once-2', 'more than once-3', 'often-4' and 'very often-5'. The scoring procedure is based on the scoring key. For the response representing 'never-1', the score is 0, for 'once-2' the score is 1, for 'more than once-3' the score is 2, for 'often-4' the score is 3 and for 'very often-5' the score is 4. Reliability & Validity With regard to the 80 individuals with two or more raters, the split-half approach was used to evaluate the reliability of the scale. According to this, the peer-rated global altruism measure had an interrater reliability of $r(78) = +0.39$ ($P < 0.01$) and the peer-rated SRA scale altruism scores had an interrater reliability of $r(78) = +0.51$ ($P < 0.01$). The 20-item SRA scale's internal consistency was also determined, and it was quite high (Cronbach alpha = 0.89, $N = 416$). By using the Spearman correlational formula to evaluate the SRA scale's validity, it was discovered that $r(86) = 0.54$.

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Results & Discussion

The analysis was done to assess the significant difference between groups regarding age, gender, location, socioeconomic status, education, family type and birth order. The independent sample 't' test was used to calculate the difference between the two groups and one-way ANOVA was used to assess the difference among more than two groups. To evaluate the relationship between the two variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient was utilised.

Table I shows the difference between two groups

Variables	Group	N	Mean	S.D	t	P	
Age	1	13-15years	42	1.0000	.00000	-18.887	.000*
	2	16-18years	58	1.8966	.30720		
Gender	1	Male	50	2.0000	.00000	34.293	.004*
	2	Female	50	1.0400	.19795		
Location	1	Rural	63	1.8254	.38268	13.092	.000*
	2	Urban	37	1.0000	.00000		
Education	1	8th -10th std	44	1.0000	.00000	-23.676	.000*
	2	11th&12th std	56	1.9286	.25987		
FamilyType	1	Nuclear	73	1.3425	.47782	-7.128	.000*
	2	Joint	27	2.0000	.00000		

*Significant at 0.05 level

From Table I, it is evidenced of the significant difference between the two groups concerning age, gender, location, education and family type. The results indicated that the respondents differ in their level of altruism based on age, gender, location, education and family type ,since the P level is less than 0.05 ,which is statistically significant. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of altruism based on gender, location, education and family type. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table II shows the difference among groups

Variables	Group	N	Mean	S.D	F	P	
Socioeconomic	1	Low	32	1.8387	.00000	49.858	.000*
	2	Middle	52	1.0000	.49125		
Status	3	High	16	1.0000	.00000		
		Total	100	1.5200	.05021		
Birth order	1	1st Child	62	1.8387	.37080	95.836	.000*
	2	2nd Child	27	1.0000	.00000		
	3	3rd Child	11	1.0000	.00000		
	Total	100	1.5200	.05021			

*Significant at 0.05 level

Table II shows the Mean, SD, 'F'values, and P-value. The second hypothesis is 'There will be no significant difference based on Socioeconomic status and birth order in the level of altruism'. While analyzing the above results there is a significant difference seen among groups in socioeconomic status and birth order in the level of altruism, as confirmed by the p-value which is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of altruism based on socioeconomic status and birth order. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table III shows the correlation between education and altruism

		Education	Altruism
Education	Pearson Correlation	1	.923**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Altruism	Pearson Correlation	.923**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

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Table III shows Pearson's correlation coefficient between education and altruism. The third hypothesis is 'There is no significant relationship between education and altruism. It is known that education and altruism are positively correlated which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore there is a significant relationship between education and altruism. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected.

Findings & Conclusion

From the study, it is known that multicultural education plays an important role in developing altruism, especially with school students. From the responses, it is known that the age groups, from 13 to 15 are low in altruism whereas, from 16 to 18 years, the respondents are high in altruism. Regarding gender, male respondents are high in altruism than female respondents. Based on location, the respondents from rural areas are more altruistic than the respondents from urban areas. While analyzing data with regards to education, it is known that higher secondary students are high in altruism than middle and high school students. Based on Family type, the respondents who are from joint families are very much more altruistic than nuclear family respondents. With regards to socioeconomic status, the respondents from low socioeconomic status are high in altruism than middle and high socioeconomic status. While analyzing responses with regards to birth order, the first-born respondents are greater in altruism than the second-born and third-born. From the findings, it is further interpreted that when educational qualification increases, altruism also increases, which is an outsourcing to the people. Other demographic variables such as age, and gender are intrinsic. Respondent's altruism based on location and family type is considered as social learning. The findings from socio-economic status are a present scenario of the respondents, that may vary with some other respondents. Therefore when a person is educated as multicultural, it will increase the level of altruism, which is needed to this society. None other demographic variables are interrelated like education with altruism. While assessing the relationship between education and altruism, there has been a positive correlation seen, which is also statistically significant at 0.01 level. Therefore when education increases altruism also increases. Thus altruism is an outcome of multicultural education which is also inter dependable.

Study Limitations & Future Recommendations

Time restrictions made it impossible to study with more samples. Some of the demographic parameters were excluded, as this study was done with school students. Only respondents from 13 to 18 were included in the study. Studying other positive personality qualities is an option. Social and cultural perspectives can be introduced with a current viewpoint.

References

- [1] Altruism (n.). Etymology. (n.d.). Retrieved January 25, 2023, from <https://www.etymonline.com/word/altruism>
- [2] Batson, C. D., Ahmad, N., & Stocks, E. L. (2011). Four forms of prosocial motivation.
- [3] Egoism, altruism, collectivism, and principlism. Psychology Press.
- [4] Baumeister, R. F., & Bushman, B. J. (2011). Social Psychology and human nature. Wadsworth.
- [5] Brief, A. P., & Motowidlo, S. J. (1986). Prosocial organizational behaviours. *Academy of Management Review*, 11(4), 710–725. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1986.4283909>
- [6] Darity, W. A. (2008). *International encyclopedia of the social sciences*. Vol. 1 (2nd ed.). Detroit: Macmillan Reference USA. pp. 87–88
- [7] Dunning, D. (2011). Social Motivation. Psychology Press.

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INTENTION AND ENLARGEMENT OF ONTOLOGY ESTABLISHED E-LEARNING SYSTEM OF SPORTS DOMAIN

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Abstract

This paper highly focused on the E-learning system is an Internet-based learning process it uses internet technology to design, implement, select, manage, support and extend learning, which will not replace traditional education methods, but will greatly improve the efficiency of education. E-learning has a lot of advantages like flexibility, diversity, measurement, openness, and etc. E-Learning has grown organically without a clear picture of the components of a typical E-learning system. E-learning in this work provides training activity for the sports domain. This aims to provide the learning activity for various learners of the sports community from different sports domain such as games and athletics. In this E-learning system, the instructor and the learner are the active participants. Knowledge of the learner through the E-learning system. There exist two types of E-learning system. In the first type, the two way communication takes place between the learner and the e-system, and in the second type it is between the learner and the instructor through the E-learning system. The total framework of the E-learning system is deployed based on the learner's key. Based on the key value the E-learning system searches the respective sports domain ontology. If the system is able to find out the correct ontology, then the output will be sent to the learner. The aim of an E-learning system is to fulfil the requirements of the learners and instructors, in order to complete the task and to win the goal.

Keywords: *E-learning, Sports Domain, Ontology.*

Introduction

The Internet and the World Wide Web have become dominant everywhere in recent years, surpassing all other technological developments in history. Currently the usage of internet is not restricted to any domain. Education is a highly significant domain where the internet is used extensively, to enhance and improve the quality of the teaching learning process.

E-Learning System

E-Learning or Web-based learning is becoming a research area, in which the web and learning converge at all levels, whether in the elementary school, college, or business. The rapid development of e-Learning is based on the astounding growth of the internet and the emergence of new advanced technologies. E-learner may have access to all kinds of learning materials 24 hours a day, seven days a week, at any possible location around the world. The rapid growth of web based courses for education and training impose challenges to e-learning systems, to generate content according to the level of the learner. Online learning or e-learning provides flexible learning alternatives compared to the traditional classroom learning, such as the possibility for the E-learners to gain knowledge at their own pace, without being constrained by location or time. In an e-learning system, the presentation of the content could reach the e-learner easily.

Sports E-learning System

Physical education and sports, represent a very interesting area characterized by interdisciplinary. Sports provided by the different related sciences, such as human and social sciences, biomechanics, mathematics, management and so on. Jinga (2003) and ICT (2004) had discussed by informatics, which has discovered in the physical education and sports a huge application area. According to Popa (1993), Derard (2000) and Epuran (2005), build up the competences required by modern technology, both to the education benefit and for an assisted sports training process. Competences efficiently to use computer tools when designing, teaching and evaluating the physical education and sports discipline and to draw up functional products, able to enhance pupils' attractiveness to the physical education and sports. Teachers' specialty competences in physical education and sports field at the theoretical level to identify the possibilities of using audio-visual aids in the educational process specific to physical education and sports field. The education process based on the e-learning system provides the learners more and more frequent opportunities to acquire new competences as presented by Grigore (2005).

Physiological Variables In Sports

The role of the physiological variables is very important. In sports, the physiological variable plays a

vital role. The physiological variable of an e-learner decides whether he/she is capable of performing the e-learners' sports training activity. Training promotes self-confidence and tolerance for higher sports levels and competition. The dynamics of training involves the manipulation of the training load through the variables: intensity, duration and frequency. In addition, sports activities are a combination of strength, speed and endurance, executed in a coordinated and efficient manner with the development of sport (Morgan et al 1987). Athletics is a major factor that determines an athlete's shape, and at a higher level, an athlete may perform and attain results close to the e-learner's maximum potential as presented by Bompa (1999). During a competition, physiological peaking is critical for optimal results and represents a point in time, when fitness and fatigue differences are maximized in favor of the overall performance outcome, as claimed by Banister and Calvert (1980). In order to improve skill and performance in competition, athletes must prepare a training process where the physiological objective is to improve the body function and optimize performance. The training process involves the repetition of exercises, designed to induce automation in the execution of a motor skill, and develop structural and metabolic functions that lead to increased physical performance. Viru (1995), reported that the goal of training is to increase the ability to sustain the highest power output or speed of movement for a given distance or time. According to Hawley (2002) the training process, overcoming training and competition stresses promotes will power, self-confidence and tolerance for higher training and competition demands, as stated by Schmolinsky (1996). Ganong (2000) stated that the control of the heart rate is mediated by the sympathetic and parasympathetic nerves.

Ontology for Sports

The system builds a Sports Domain Ontology that enables to extract sports news from sports related web sites. Especially, the football league is the main target of the system. Ontology is the basis of representing the semantic information for a particular domain. Rashmi Chauhan et al (2012), proposed a conceptual model for ontology based semantic information retrieval, and constructed an ontology for the sports domain. Query expansion techniques have been broadly applied for information retrieval. A semantic query expansion technique that includes a mathematical model to compute the semantic Similarity between concepts and an algorithm for query expansion, based on domain ontology, is designed. To provide an efficient sports e-learning system based on physiological variables and physical training activity.

- 1) To provide ontological support for enhancing the keyword queries given by the e-learner.
- 2) Developing and implementing an efficient CSP for the knowledge representation of physiological variables for sports-learners.
- 3) To formalize the sports activity learning through planning and scheduling.

Design of an E-Learning System for the Sports Domain

E-Learning system for the sports domain and the physiological variables are interrelated with each other. A sports e-learner needs to have knowledge about these relationships. Through this sports e-learning system, the e-learner can efficiently query and improve his knowledge of the physiological variable and physical activity training. The e-learning system responds to any correct keywords, by matching the ontology, and stores the information in the query template. The query template plays an efficient role, as it can respond to repeated queries with minimal time. The e-learning system uses the indexed query template and responds immediately. An e-learner of the sports domain may have different values for the various physiological variables.

Conclusion

The sports e-learning system is an emerging area which requires a specialized approach compared to e-learning in other domain, in the sense that sports learning is not just a mere knowledge transfer, it includes physical activity and performances in events. This paper focused the physiological variable into consideration for the sports e-learner to plan and schedule the task in future based on the behavioral facial expression. The physiological variable can also be used to understand the psychology of the e-learner.

References

- [1] Bistra, N., Dilkina, William, S. and Havens, "The U.S. National Football League Scheduling Problem", 2004, American Association for Artificial Intelligence.
- [2] Carlson, A., Betteridge, J., Kisiel, B., Settles, B., Hruschka, E.R. and Mitchell, T.M. "Toward an Architecture for Never-Ending Language Learning", AAAI, 2010.
- [3] Ganong, W. "Review of Medical Physiology", A Lange Medical Book, USA, pp.550, 2000.

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THE ROLE OF GENDER EQUALITY IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education is commonly recognized to advantage individuals and encourage national development. Educating females and males leads to similar increases in their subsequent earnings and develops future opportunities and selections for both boys and girls. However, educating girls produces many additional socio-economic advances that benefit the entire communities. These benefits include increased economic productivity, higher family incomes, delayed marriages, reduced fertility rates, and improved health and survival rates for infants and children. The main purpose of this research paper is to understand gender equality in education. Over the years, education has focused on access and equality. While inadequate attention has been paid to retention and achievement and the quality or the relevance to education. The promotion of gender equality within the educational institutions, leads to a higher enrolment and retention rate and it helps to ensure that males and females of all age groups are able to acquire benefits of education.

Keywords: *Gender Equality, Education, Teaching and Learning Processes, Educational Institutions, Students*

Introduction

Gender is a social concept that has an influence upon the approaches, parts, accountabilities and behaviour patterns of boys and girls, and men and women in all societies. Gender relations differ in societies. It is a women's and people's issues formed by power relations in multicultural societies like India. It deals with human concerns incorporating diversities and variations. It has been the most prevalent form of discrimination operating across cultures in developed and developing societies. When one researches upon the present framework of gender discourses, the prime concern is how gender functions as an element of making an improvement in knowledge. Education has the inherent potential of introducing social change in the framework of gender relations. Therefore, cognizant and varied interventions have been put forward by the Government of India to address gender equality in education at the centre and state level. A momentous initiative was undertaken in 1986, with the enactment of the National Policy on Education (NPE) and its revised POA 1992. This philosophy has also been reflected in the National Policy on Empowerment of Women 2001 (Srivastava, n.d.). Gender equality in education has been revealed within the curriculum frameworks developed by the apex national organization like National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT). In this regard curriculum frameworks of 1975, 1988, 2000 and 2005 have made precise efforts to put emphasis on gender disparities in education. The journey has been from the feelings of apprehension to considerable inclusion. While numerous efforts have been made on integrating gender concerns in education; globalization, liberalization and expansion in information technology have once again made it mandatory for reconsidering gender concerns in education in a proactive manner as a vital developmental program. Gender debates and discourses have been put into operation within the overarching concern for democratizing education (Srivastava, n.d.).

Gender Equity in Education in India

Gender equity in education in India aims to take into account the educational access concerns affecting both girls and boys within the country in the field of education and the types of initiatives that are needed to secure meaningful and a sustainable access to all. Both the data and the research literature that have been obtained are analysed to put emphasis upon the interconnecting nature of the educational additions and omissions. Viewing gendered access alongside concerns such as education of the children belonging to the scheduled caste, scheduled tribes, Other Backward Classes and Muslims, disability, deprived, marginalized and socio-economically backward sections of the society, poverty and child labour. Supply side concerns are also discussed in terms of the provision of education and gendered schooling practices. Creativities planned to address the gendered inequalities are then highlighted and critiqued (Bandhyopadhyay, & Subrahmanian, 2008). India accounts for 30% of the world's total illiterate population and around 70% of these illiterates are women. As per 2001 Census data, women constitute 48% of the total population within the country, but around 46% of women are still found to be illiterate. Problems of gender disparity and discrimination begin with access to education. The Gender Parity Index (GPI) at the primary and upper primary levels was 0.9 and 0.8 in 2003. This remained more or less the same in 2005-06, for primary GPI was 0.92 and for upper primary 0.84. Once the girls are able to get enrolled in schools, they are rather more expected than the boys to continue their education in an efficient way. Access and maintenance problems develop at the higher levels of education with the GPI at lower secondary and upper secondary levels dropping to 0.73 and 0.67 respectively (Bandhyopadhyay, & Subrahmanian, 2008).

Female education has long been recognized to create strong correlations with the other dimensions of human and social development. The low levels of education meaningfully affect the health and nutritional status of women. For instance, in India, if the women will not possess education or enhance their literacy skills, they will not be able to accomplish something in their lives. When there will be enhancement of education amongst the women, then the cases of suffering from the diseases caused by malnutrition would decline progressively with the increased levels of education. Height and Body Mass Index (BMI) differ with levels of education and illiterate women are reportedly at more risk of having lower height and BMI, leading to higher deficiency of iron and other nutrients. Similarly, while 56% of the illiterate women suffer from anaemia, the percentage declines to 40% in the case of the women who have obtained at least high school education (Bandhyopadhyay, &Subrahmanian, 2008).

There has been strong economic and social evidence of the high returns to the education of women. Most of the communities continue to under-invest in the education of the women. In the pursuance of the primary education, there has been narrowing in the gender gaps. On the other hand, in the secondary and higher education, discriminatory treatment against the women and children continue to exist. Economic and social privilege also affect the gendered patterns of access, with girls in secondary and higher education that primarily came from higher income and social groups, are offered higher social status (Bandhyopadhyay, &Subrahmanian, 2008). The women and girls who belong to marginalized communities and low socio-economic groups are considered disadvantaged and they are discriminated against. It is believed that females belonging to deprived and disadvantaged communities do not possess the abilities to understand, they are slow learners and it is difficult to provide them any kind of training or instructions. The profoundly entrenched undervaluation of female labour, recognized mainly with the reproductive or the household province, motivates the confidence in many communities that educating women would bring low returns, as abilities required in the reproductive sphere require domestic socialization and not many years of schooling. The gender division of labour continues to reward women less within the workplace. This has resulted in moderately lower female education and work participation reproducing the ideological bias against considering women as the heads of the household and primary care givers. Low valuation of women as labourers in the market place and association of female labour with satisfying domestic responsibilities including child rearing has led to a deep-rooted cultural association of women with the institutions of marriage and family (Bandhyopadhyay, &Subrahmanian, 2008).

Gender Equality: A Conceptual Framework for Reaching all the Learners

Gender equality is an often used term but it is occasionally defined. Translating the concept of gender equality in education into a concrete background will assist the education programmers to perform the functions of planning, managing, and evaluating the education projects. To be practical, this framework must draw clear differences and establish interrelationships amongst the perceptions of gender parity, gender equity, and gender equality. In addition to drawing out the distinctions between equity and equality, the framework also supports other key issues in education such as access, superiority, continuousness, and significance. Gender equality means that males and females have equal opportunities to recognize their complete human rights and contribute to and benefit from economic, social, cultural, and political development. Equality and justice are the building blocks of equivalence in education (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008).

There have been opening of new gender gaps in the field of education. Young men as compared to young women are enrolled in school to a lesser extent. They have poor academic skills and low educational achievements (The ABC of Gender Equality in Education Attitude, Behaviour, Confidence, 2015). In the field of education, there is a difference between gender parity and gender equality. Parity is acquired when the same proportion of girls and boys are enrolled in schools and educational institutions with an aim of enhancing their educational qualifications, skills and abilities and achieving educational goals. For the achievement of gender equality, reaching parity within the system of education is necessary. Gender equality is referred to the process of providing equal and fair treatment to the girls and boys. To ensure fairness, there must be formulation of measures to compensate the historical and the social advantages that prevent the girls and the boys from participating on the same area (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008).

Within the classroom setting, the attitude of the teachers towards the students is primarily on the basis of their performance. The performance may be academic performance, their way of interaction with the individuals, their behaviour, attitude and approaches, attendance and decorum. The student, who is good in all areas scores well and earns appreciation from his teachers. On the other hand, students who are weak in certain areas achieve low grades. The differences in the scores of the students does not mean that the teachers are discriminating against them. Equity does not imply treating all the learners in a similar manner, the reason being, there are many factors that would lead to the disadvantages of the students in having a chance to achieve equitable results (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008).

Within the classroom and the educational institution, to acquire appreciation, the students are

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required to effectively implement the necessary areas in an operative manner. The individual's accomplishments are determined by his or her capabilities and efforts. In educational institutions, support and assistance from the teachers is considered to be imperative to enhance one's performance. The teachers do make efforts and regard all the students equal. It is unlawful to discriminate against anybody. On the other hand, it is up to the students to implement proper decorum within the classroom and in the educational institution. Discipline is an imperative area and to maintain discipline, students are required to give respect and communicate in an efficient manner with the other individuals. An efficient strategy for providing education to the girls also includes attention to parity and equality simultaneously. In addition, involvements on behalf of the girls should be incorporated into a rational and a logical complete approach of the educational reform (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008).

Dimensions of Gender Equality in Education

There are four main dimensions of gender equality in education (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008). Equality of Access – Equality of access means that girls and boys within the schools and other educational institutions should be made available equal opportunities to acquire admission in the formal, informal, non-formal and other alternative approaches to basic education. The attendance of the students is regarded to be the main area, which identifies that whether access has been achieved. To obtain access, it is vital that students should have an appropriate means of transportation available. If the schools are at a walking distance to the homes, this gives them pleasure and satisfaction to a large extent. Awareness of the parents should be raised, they should be made aware of the rights and responsibilities that they have towards the education of their children. In addition to basic numeracy and literacy skills, it is vital that students should have access to health and well-being, democracy, good governance, conflict management, and self-discovery. It is vital to make provision of scholarships for the students, especially belonging to disadvantaged communities. Training of the communities to monitor access and quality through the parent-teacher associations and the school management committees, ensuring that women are part of the management. Improving the capability of the schools to make provision of educational services through education financemechanisms that increase expenditure on quality inputs such as textbooks and decrease parental payments that may impede student attendance. Equality of Educational Outcomes - Equality of educational outcomes means that girls and boys are made availableequal opportunities to accomplishand consequences are based on their individual aptitudes and determinations. To ensure rationalopportunities for achievement, the length of school professions, academic qualifications, and diplomas should not differ based on a person's gender. Devicesfor evaluating individual achievement should also be free of any gender bias. What tests, examinations, and assessments measure tells

Students what matters and to the extent that these mechanismsreflect a gender bias, they convey messages to the students that can discourage their attention in school or in particular subjects. Results from the classroom tests, national examinations, and international assessments can have an influence on the confidence levels of the boys and girls and theopinions of their abilities and what is expected of them. They can also impact what is taught in the classroom and how content is distributed. Where tests or examinations are used to control promotion into future grades, or other types ofeducational opportunities, the extent to which there may be bias in these devices is an important consideration when trying to ensure equality of access and equality of outcomes. Equality of External Results - Equality of external results takes place when the status of men and women, their access to products, services and resources, and their ability to contribute to, participate in, and benefit from economic, social, cultural, and political activities are equal. This entails that career opportunities, the time needed to protected employment after leaving full-time education, and the incomes of men and women with similar qualifications andexperience are equal. The four dimensions of gender equality are related, but the relationship is multifaceted and not necessarily direct. Equivalence in enrolment and greater gender equality in schooling can, and often co-exist with variations outside of education. In fact, several studies have established that educational achievement for girls does not mechanicallytransform into higher economic status or greater political participation as adults.

Tools for the Gender Responsive Educational Environment

Attitudes of the teachers and school administrators, as well as the prejudiced curriculum and teaching, learning materials, often prove to be problems within the course of equal learning made available to the girls and boys. Gender sensitive education, on the other hand, is one that treats women and men and girls and boys equally and encourages them to realize their complete potential. Gender sensitive approaches and learning materials encourage non-stereotyped images of women and men, which are crucial for generating a learning atmosphere that is reasonable and maintainable for all the individuals. Teachers and other facilitators must be aware of student's needs, who are both men and women. There is a need to redress this inequalityand eliminate the areas that may prove to be barriers within the course of gender equality (Promoting Gender Equality in Education, 2009). This gender lens is envisioned for all the individuals involved in the process of formulation

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of the curriculum and teaching and learning processes. It includes the areas that need to be reflected upon at every stage of the process of generating resources and the curriculum. This gender lens should provide assistance to all the individuals who are involved in school management. These include not only the project or programme people, but also teachers and school heads to reflect in a better way on the gender sensitivity and responsiveness of the educational institutions. They can in a more efficient way, make all the essential transformations so that gender equality prevails within the educational institutions (Promoting Gender Equality in Education, 2009). To promote gender equality, the individuals are required to be determined within their mind-sets. The strong determination of the individuals would largely contribute in the promotion of gender equality. Within schools, students come to learn, they attend classes of different subjects as well as get involved in extra-curricular activities. In classrooms, teachers have a vital role to play. They are considered to be the individuals who play an important part in the shaping of the success and failure of the students. Their interpretation of the curriculum and the instructional methods, communication with the students, and way they allocate duties, homework assignments and conduct class tests and exams, are important factors in the attainment of education. The attitude and approaches of the teachers have to be framed in such a manner that students should feel that they are approachable, amiable and considerate in their attitude. The teachers are the first and the foremost individuals that need to promote gender equality in education. Above the teachers, there are the directors, principals, head teachers, who make provision of ideas and suggestions to them (Promoting Gender Equality in Education, 2009). The teachers are required to follow the guidelines and the instructions that they receive from their superiors.

Teaching and Learning Processes in Education

Text and instructional materials at the secondary stage have sharper forms related to science, social science, languages and mathematics. It is important that at this stage, children are able to acquire knowledge and information entrenched in different subjects, apply the knowledge to understand their living realities, and are capable and experienced enough to interconnect, convey and critically understand their surroundings from a gender perspective. While teaching the subjects at the secondary stage, the pedagogical methods have to be well organized for making the classrooms, in various settings, genders sensitive (Srivastava, n.d.). In schools as well as in higher educational institutions, there is prevalence of co-education. In this type of education, men and women, girls and boys are together part of the educational institutions. In co-education, important areas that are required to be taken into consideration are, males and females should be provided with equal opportunities and there should not be any discrimination between them. Evaluation should be on the basis of the performance of the students. Within the classrooms and educational institutions, the students are required to interact amongst themselves. They not just come to schools to enhance their academic qualifications, but also learn a number of other areas, such as, communication, manners and etiquettes, decorum and coping up with the difficulties and problems. Classroom interactions have an important influence upon the personalities of the children. The methodology that has been adopted in the impartment of the content, related to many spheres of knowledge, not only stimulates learning and understanding but also overall personality of the students. In the framework of gender equality, involvement of the children in negotiations, dialogs, group discussions, problem solving, diverse activities and articulation of their uncertainties and experiences are the ways of breaking gender barriers related to caste, class, region and location. In the teaching and learning of different subjects offered to the students at the secondary stage of education, one may consider some suggested gender inclusive undertakings. In the teaching and the learning processes, the instructors are required to formulate the techniques and adopt the methods with regards to the gender differences. It is vital to explain the concepts with clarity and examples. In some of the areas, girls and boys are provided with different examples and ideas. The use of the teaching aids should be used as readily as possible. Within the classroom setting, where there are both girls and boys, then it is vital to make use of effective teaching aids that would facilitate their learning in an appropriate manner. The viewpoints of prominent researchers who have talked about gender equality should be taken into account. It is vital to make the teaching and the learning processes more dialogical and encourage teamwork. It is vital to make use of techniques for enhanced participation and involvement. Students should be provided with the opportunities to give ideas and suggestions. Teachers should help the students in providing solutions to all their problems and concerns. In educational institutions, inappropriate acts may take place between students, hence, it is vital that they should treat each other in an appropriate manner.

Challenges within the Gender Equality in Education

The area of education experiences a number of challenges with regards to gender equality. Girls and women are deprived in a number of ways. Although changes in the government policies and application of more holistic strategies are required. There are also minor procedures and actions that can be undertaken when added together, and can contribute to changes in practice in the direction of larger gender equality in education. Nevertheless, all the impediments for democratic conduct of girls and women in education, there are

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many examples of successful projects and programmes. In some of the educational institutions, there is discriminatory treatment against Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and Other Backward Classes. Particularly the girls belonging to these communities are not provided with the similar kinds of opportunities as compared to students belonging to the other groups. (Gender Equality in and through Education, 2010). At the higher level of education, there is a wider gender gap. Girls dropping out of school and discontinuing their higher education and remaining behind the boys in class performances and in the retention rates were the issues of highest concern not only in India, but in other countries as well. Access to secondary education was stated as one of the largest problems and one of the main reasons for the lower enrolment of girls in secondary education. Secondary schools are primarily located in the urban areas or in district centres, which implies that students either have to walk a long distance to school or have to stay in dormitories for the entire weeks, months or semesters. In either case, this situation affects girls more than boys. Girls are more susceptible to insecurity and unsafe roads and within the dormitories too, the girls often feel insecure (Gender Equality in and through Education, 2010). The drop out of girls was higher than the boys, as it is obvious, students need proper facilities within the schools to facilitate learning. The conditions of the schools were in a more deprived state in rural areas as compared to the urban.

The teachers within the educational institutions should be properly trained regarding gender equality. In most cases, teachers prove themselves to be treating all the students equally and not discriminating against anybody. Teachers do lack gender awareness and this is stated to be a concerning issue. In some cases, the term gender equality was misunderstood by the term of gender parity. Teachers are unaware of gender sensitive teaching methodologies and neither do teacher trainers know about it. Gender stereotyping is communal and textbooks are frequently gender biased. The commonly deprived quality of teaching and teachers' low qualifications in a negative manner affect a gender sensitive pedagogy. There have been studies conducted on the attitude of the teachers regarding the gender roles and the relationship of the teachers with the boys and girls students. It has been observed that teachers pay more attention to the male students, provide more feedback to them and communicate with them in an effective manner (Gender Equality in and through Education, 2010). The girls need to get more encouraged. They mainly feel more vulnerable within the educational institutions as compared to boys, hence, teachers need to pay equal attention to them and make attempts to solve their problems.

In rural areas, the families encourage the education of the boys, they possess this viewpoint that boys should be provided with good education and training, so that they are able to obtain an appropriate employment opportunity. The boys are regarded to be the assets and should be encouraged to acquire education. In the present existence, the rural masses have been communicated about this viewpoint that girls should be treated equal as compared to the boys. They should be provided with complete freedom to attend schools and enhance their educational qualifications. The girls in urban and rural areas get enrolled in schools, but besides education, they also have to do the household chores. The boys are given complete time to study, whereas girls have lesser time to devote towards studies (Gender Equality in and through Education, 2010). There is a high rate of absenteeism amongst the girls as compared to the boys; the girls have more responsibilities than the boys, hence, the implementation of other tasks and functions leads to an increase in the rate of absenteeism.

Recommendations

The recommendations to bring about gender equality in education have been stated as follows: (Education from a Gender Equality Perspective, 2008). It is vital to make sure that gender concerns are identified and addressed at the highest level of politics and public policy. Within the educational institutions, it is necessary that gender concerns need to be identified and accordingly adequate procedures should be put into practice. When proper measures and policies will be put into operation, then within the schools and higher educational institutions, there will be prevalence of gender equality. Therefore, one of the important areas is to identify the gender concerns. Identification of the numerous entry points for speaking about gender inequalities, which include enrolment strategies, guidelines and practices, curriculum relevance, position of the teachers, learning environments, security, new technologies, and resource allocation. These areas are imperative for leading to success of the educational institution. When attempts have been made to promote gender equality, it is necessary to make sure that all the guidelines, technologies, resources and so forth should be allocated equally amongst the girls and the boys. Ensure that gender concerns are recognized and addressed in the actions that are putting emphasis on the global issues such as HIV/AIDS and education in predicaments or post-conflict situations. There are occurrence of problems and difficulties in the lives of the students. Due to these, they need assistance and suggestions from their teachers and the counsellors. They are required to treat all students equally and provide valuable and meaningful suggestions to them in accordance to their problems.

Conclusion

Significant consideration has been paid to improving access and quality at the primary level,

however, there is some indication that secondary level education may provide higher returns, especially for girls. The financial returns to schooling at the secondary and tertiary levels are steadily high and differentially high for young women. The opening between the returns to higher and lower levels of schooling is growing, thus placing an increasing premium on secondary and tertiary schooling for later achievement in the labour market. Within the educational institutions, the students belong to different castes, classes, ethnicities, religious groups, and socio-economic backgrounds. In order to provide education in an appropriate manner, it is vital to treat all the students equally and not discriminate between them. If primary school enrolment and completion rates are high, but there is not any prevalence of gender equality, then this may lead to detrimental consequences. Absence of gender equality will obstruct the learning and understanding of the students within the schools. It will also impede the promotion of job satisfaction amongst the teachers and the staff and lead to a decline in the enrolment rates. Access, duration, and quality are the crucial variables in realizing educational benefits. The promotion of gender equality will provide satisfaction to not only the students but also the teachers and the staff members. The students will take pleasure in getting enrolled in schools. They will feel pleasure in interacting with the students around and enhancing their skills and abilities in an effective manner. Therefore, besides the performance of the work duties, efforts should be made to promote gender equality in education.

References

- [1] Bandhyopadhyay, M., & Subrahmanian, R. (2008). Gender Equity in Education: A Review of Trends and Factors. National University of Educational Planning and Administration. Retrieved January 01, 2018 from http://www.createrpc.org/pdf_documents/PTA18.pdf
- [2] Education from a Gender Equality Perspective. (2008). Retrieved January 01, 2018 from http://www.ungei.org/resources/files/Education_from_a_Gender_Equality_Perspective.pdf
- [3] Gender Equality in and through Education. (2010). Retrieved January 02, 2018 from <https://www.oecd.org/derec/sweden/48350382.pdf>
- [4] Promoting Gender Equality in Education. (2009). UNESCO. Retrieved January 02, 2018 from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001864/186495E.pdf>
- [5] Srivastava, G. (n.d.). Gender Concerns in Education. NCERT. Retrieved January 01, 2018 from http://www.ncert.nic.in/departments/nie/dse/activities/advisory_board/PDF/Genderconcerns.pdf
- [6] The ABC of Gender Equality in Education Attitude, Behaviour, Confidence. (2015).
- [7] Retrieved January 02, 2018 from <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/keyfindings/pisa-2012-results-gender-eng.pdf>

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GLOBAL INTERCULTURE EDUCATION AND ITS POINTS OF CONTENTION AND INTERRELATIONSHIPS

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Abstract

The contemporary society is a versatile society described by variety and change. The issue of dwelling together is progressively moved toward in the cutting edge society. We have a place with various ethnic gatherings, different semantic societies and strict foundations. Considering this variety, conjunction is a must. Intercultural schooling is one of the fundamental devices with which individuals from the general public and social orders. Intercultural instruction is a worldwide need, a particular type of training that puts people and their societies in places of differential treatment, and yet they are in places of equity. Intercultural instruction is a component of the new training, which centers around the values referenced previously. It advances fortitude of the nearby local area with the worldwide local area.

Keywords: *Human culture, political, economic, education, social standard, conduct, dress, language.*

Introduction

In a world experiencing rapid change, and where cultural, political, economic and social upheaval challenges traditional ways of life, education has a major role to play in promoting social cohesion and peaceful coexistence. Through programmes that encourage dialogue between students of different cultures, beliefs and religions, education can make an important and meaningful contribution to sustainable and tolerant societies. Intercultural Education is a response to the challenge to provide quality education for all. It is framed within a Human Rights perspective as expressed in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948): Education shall be directed to the full development of human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial and religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace. UNESCO's mission in the field of education is to guide educational policy worldwide, with the goal of ensuing universal primary education for all by the year 2015. However, the idea of universality is shifting and complex. The governability of pluralistic, democratic societies increasingly depends on the capacity of governments to provide equity in public and social life, and to educate citizens who are open to intercultural dialogue and tolerant of each other's ways of being and thinking.

Main Points of Contention and Interrelationship Sculture

Culture is an umbrella term which envelops the social way of behaving, establishments, and standards tracked down in human social orders, as well as the information, convictions, expressions, regulations, customs, capacities, and propensities for the people in these gatherings. Culture is frequently started from or credited to a particular district or area. People obtain culture through the growing experiences of enculturation and socialization, which is shown by the variety of societies across social orders. A social standard classifies satisfactory lead in the public eye; it fills in as a rule for conduct, dress, language, and disposition in a circumstance, which fills in as a layout for assumptions in a gathering. Culture is characterized in various ways. Thusly, it has been characterized as "the entire arrangement of signs by which the individuals from a given society recognize...one another, while recognizing them from individuals not having a place with that society.

Culture and Education

The roles of educational institutions, teachers, and instructive materials in a social development and change are for the general development of a human being. Every individual of the general public has their own inclination and mindset to see the world around. Training changes the view of the person toward various types of local area. Training is by all accounts a groundwork of the transmission, and on occasion, the change of culture. Understanding this collaboration is complicated, to some degree since "training" and "culture" are challenging to depict with accuracy; and to a limited extent in light of the fact that the cooperation heads down the two paths: culture affects schooling alongside, extraordinary effect of instruction on culture.

Culture and Language

Language issues are key to culture. Dialects result from a verifiable and aggregate insight and express socially specific perspectives and worth frameworks. Estimates 7 which recommend that a portion of the 6,000 dialects spoken in this present reality are at risk for vanishing are a reason to worry, for they ensnare the vanishing of the related societies with which they are so intently tied, as well as the information frameworks

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held inside them. Language issues are likewise vital to ideas of schooling. Etymological abilities are central for the strengthening of the person in fair and plural social orders, as they condition school accomplishment, elevate admittance to different societies and urge receptiveness to social trade.

Culture and Region

Different religions, faiths and attitudes to spirituality stand as collective and historical creations which “reflect the diversity of human experience and the various ways people have of coming to terms with the promise, challenge and tragedy of human life”. Vote based social orders genuinely must resolve between strict issues through schooling. These issues presently have a place with the instructive plan in numerous nations all through the world. However it is vital to take note of the significance of an interfaith part inside Intercultural Instruction is setting specific. As a mentality to otherworldliness, secularism is seemingly a worth situation on a standard to religion, and is the standard in certain nations, where the state has advanced the school as a space liberated from strict imagery and doctrine. In a mainstream social school setting, interfaith training may not convey a similar weight and significance as it would in a climate where issues of confidence highlight vigorously in school life.

Cultural Diversity and Cultural Heritage

Social variety shapes part of a financial and political setting and is connected with power structures that impact the manners by which parts of the world's social legacy are seen and socially developed. The different social networks that form an express, a country, or any human culture have inconsistent admittance to political and monetary power and impact. Frequently clashes between various social gatherings are related with financial and political elements, by which social distinction might be a trait albeit not really a causal component. Moreover, 21st century society is multicultural generally. However various societies don't have similar opportunities for endurance or articulation in the cutting edge world. With regards to political struggle and continually evolving conditions, they advance and adjust, with a more open to change.

Majority and Minority Cultures

Social essentialness is firmly connected to the social and financial status of minority networks. This is on the grounds that the social elements of various networks, like practices, convictions, or ways of life, are 'esteemed' and hierarchized. And keeping in mind that some win, others are underestimated. The social piece of social orders is today developing considerably additional complex through expanding transitory developments starting with one country then onto the next and from rustic to metropolitan locales. While native people groups and other minority gatherings can think back on a long verifiable custom in a given locale, the present transient developments will quite often create socially divided, normally metropolitan or semi-metropolitan social orders, which present explicit difficulties for instructive strategies.

Multiculturalism and Interculturalism

To reinforce a majority rules government, schooling systems need to consider the multicultural person of society, and focus on effectively adding to quiet concurrence and positive cooperation between various social gatherings. There have generally been two methodologies: multicultural instruction and Intercultural Schooling. Multicultural schooling involves finding out about different societies to create acknowledgment, or if nothing else resistance, of these societies. Intercultural Schooling expects to go past detached conjunction, to accomplish a creating and supportable approach to living respectively in multicultural social orders through the making of comprehension of, regard for and discourse between the different social gatherings.

Interculture Learning Objectives

- 1) To create intercultural responsiveness, and mindfulness, figuring out how to check out, investigate, and resolve issues according to the point of view of social contrasts.
- 2) To develop intercultural perspectives, which incorporate being open minded, conscious, inquisitive, and compassionate towards different societies.
- 3) To secure social information, both culture general and culture explicit, really focusing on the imperceptible social components, which resemble the secret piece of an ice shelf.
- 4) A definitive objective of intercultural learning is to change our mindfulness, perspectives, and information into capability, and to foster adaptability and flexibility in intercultural correspondence.

Conclusion

To develop urban ways of life and social cooperation that reinforce regard for basic liberties and obligation in the activity of individual flexibility, the aftereffects of intercultural schooling require down to earth soundness and transient point of view consciousness of the positive worth of social variety and of the

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right of the individual to be different a basic familiarity with the job that neighborhood networks and nearby information frameworks, dialects and social practices play in the growing experience and development of the individual in public, provincial and worldwide social orders information on the historical backdrop of progress and humanities to work with better comprehension and the capacity to convey the possibility of the plural, dynamic, relative and correlative nature of societies.

References

- [1] <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000147878>
- [2] <https://conference.pixel-online.net/NPSE/files/npse/ed0004/FP/1426-NTST861-FP-NPSE4.pdf>
- [3] <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/courses/intercultural-communication/0/steps/11045#:~:text=The%20ultimate%20goal%20of%20intercultural,and%20adaptability%20in%20intercultural%20communication.>
- [4] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/intercultural-education>
- [5] <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/intercultural-education/15234>
- [6] <https://adamasuniversity.ac.in/culture-and-education/#:~:text=Culture%20and%20education%20are%20two,and%20eternal%20values%20of%20life.>

PHYSICAL FITNESS AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract

Physical fitness is any activity that involves moving body. It includes everyday activities, physically active play, and organized sports and exercises. Physical activity boosts children's well-being. Being Physically active and fit holds utmost importance especially among today's younger generation who is busy enjoying the luxuries of mobile, laptop and TV at an alarming rate and aren't active and spirited on a daily basis. Physical fitness measures are closely allied with disease prevention and health promotion, thus it is common and appropriate to measure components of physical fitness before preventive and rehabilitative programs. Physical fitness can be modified through regular physical activity and exercise.

Introduction

Physical fitness is any activity that involves moving body. It includes everyday activities, physically active play, and organized sports and exercises. It can be light/moderate/vigorous physical activity, energetic play, or activities that strengthen muscles and bones. Young student have a lot of potentials to be able to develop new hobbies that can benefit fitness. It can be anything like running, skipping, swimming etc. Exercising at least four times a week increases metabolic rate which reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases in the future. Regular physical activity can improve brain health, help manage weight, reduce the risk of disease, strengthen bones and muscles and improve ability to do everyday activities. Physical fitness in children strengthens their bones, muscles, hearts, and lungs. Improves children's coordination, balance, posture, and flexibility. It also helps children maintain a healthy weight. Physical activity boosts children's well-being. For example, active children are more likely to be confident and feel like they belong as well as concentrate better at school. Physical activity is an important part of play and learning. As physical and mental fitness is a key component for students to lead a healthy lifestyle, therefore including Physical Education in the school and college curriculum. Physical fitness refers to the ability of your body systems to work together efficiently to allow you to be a healthy person and perform activities of daily living. Being physically active can improve your brain health, help manage weight, reduce the risk of disease, strengthen bones and muscles, and improve your ability to do everyday activities. Physical fitness is a set of attributes that are either health- or skill-related. Being physically fit has been defined as "the ability to carry out daily tasks with vigor and alertness, without undue fatigue and with ample energy to enjoy leisure-time pursuits and to meet unforeseen emergencies". The degree to which people have these attributes can be measured with specific tests. Physical fitness measures are closely allied with disease prevention and health promotion, thus it is common and appropriate to measure components of physical fitness before preventive and rehabilitative programs. Physical fitness can be modified through regular physical activity and exercise. Physical fitness components have been shown to have a significant positive relationship with enhanced outcomes in physical activity, including sports participation. Being Physically active and fit holds utmost importance especially among today's younger generation who is busy enjoying the luxuries of mobile, laptop and TV at an alarming rate and aren't active and spirited on a daily basis. Being involved in electronic devices aren't bad until and unless it is used as a source of entertainment for a limited time. In order to enjoy the beauty of life and to experience it to the fullest you must start getting involved in physical activities or sports. Being young, students have a lot of potential to develop a hobby that keeps their fitness regulated for the lifetime.

Benefits of Physical Fitness

Being physically fit doesn't necessarily require a rigorous schedule of workout. There are few benefits of exercising and being active are :-

- 1) Better focus in school. When the brain activates following exercise, it can better concentrate and helps improve memory and information retention. This helps students to perform better and learn more information during lessons.
- 2) Improves school attendance. Students who participate in regular physical activity are less likely to get sick and be absent. The immune system gets stronger and ready to fight illnesses better.
- 3) Better academic performance. Studies show that students who are physically active get better grades. These students also perform better on standardized tests and have higher graduation rates.
- 4) Builds a strong, healthy body. Students that develop a routine for physical activity when they are younger lower their risk of obesity, heart disease, high blood pressure, and other life-altering diseases and conditions. This helps them build a healthier and stronger body for a longer life.
- 5) Improves sleep quality. Students that participate in physical activity get better sleep and achieve

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a deeper sleep that helps their body to recover from exercise. Better sleep increases their ability to focus or concentrate their energy levels, and better manage stress.

- 6) Reduces risk of anxiety and depression. Activity helps release endorphins, feel- good hormones, that help reduce stress therefore relieving feelings of anxiety and depression.
- 7) Develops better social and problem-solving skills. Participating in activities that include working with others on a team or a group help students develop positive social and problem-solving skills. Students learn to cooperate with others, encourage teammates, and achieve a goal.
- 8) Build self-confidence. Finding a skill, activity, or sport a student can find success at helps build self-confidence which helps students try new skills, learn new information, and take risks.
- 9) More energy. A body in motion, stays in motion. When a student participates in regular physical activity, they will have more energy and be alert throughout their day. This helps them engage in their learning and enjoy class.
- 10) It's fun. It's important for all students to just have fun! Finding an activity a student enjoys and finds pleasure in will help increase the likelihood of them participating in physical activity for their lifetime.

Exercise Helps in Increasing Energy Levels

Physical exercise helps in improving the efficiency and the strength of the cardiovascular systems which enables an individual in getting more nutrients and oxygen to the muscles. This enables students to have extra energy for enjoying fun stuff in their lives.

Exercise Helps in Improving Muscle Strength

If students stay active and keep their joints, ligaments and muscles flexible, it allows them to avoid injuries and in moving more easily. Strong ligaments and joints help in reducing the chances of lower back and joint pain in students which further helps in improving their performance at school.

Physical Activity Helps in Maintaining Healthy Weight

Students who are a little obese and are unable to concentrate on their studies because of constant hunger and craving for food should always try and exercise on a regular basis. This is because exercise helps in maintaining healthy weight which improves the overall well-being of a student.

How to Promote Physical Activity in Schools

Physical activity helps students in so many ways, parents, educators and school administrators must partner to facilitate and encourage physical activity among students. Strategies to increase physical activity in schools:

Inform Students of the Benefits

By informing students of how impactful physical exercise is to their health and wellbeing, as well as their performance at school, we can motivate and empower them to stay active. This is especially important for older students since they're more capable of understanding the research on physical activity's benefits and tend to have more say over how they spend their time at home.

Inform Parents of the Benefits

Parents can also play a vital role in helping their kids stay active, especially when it comes to younger children, so schools should find opportunities to educate parents on just how beneficial physical activity is for their kids. Encourage parents to limit the time their children spend in front of a television or computer screen and instead plan activities for the whole family that involve physical exercise. Parents may also want to enrol their children in extracurricular activities to help them stay active.

Prioritize Physical Education Classes

Physical education courses give students the opportunity to get some exercise during the school day and can help them learn healthy habits for leading active lifestyles. Physical education classes that teach sports and other team-building games add a social component to physical activity that can make it more fun and meaningful for kids. Physical education classes can play an influential role for students who otherwise live sedentary lifestyles.

Build Time in the Schedule for Recess

Recess is another important way to promote physical activity at school. Whereas physical education courses are structured, recess should focus more on free play. There are various models for recess you can implement at school. It could be one recess period in the afternoon or a series of short recess periods

throughout the day.

Upgrade Playground Equipment

Having limited playground equipment does not communicate a commitment to fostering active play at school. So, take a look at your playground equipment and consider whether it could stand to be replaced, or whether you should add some new equipment.

Include Physical Movement in the Classroom

Teachers can help students stay active by incorporating physical movement into their lesson plans. For example, teachers can set up learning stations at the four corners of the room and have students walk to each station as part of the lesson. Even if teachers are intimidated by the idea of incorporating physical activity into their lesson planning, they can simply have students stand up periodically during class to stretch or “get the wiggles out” so they can focus.

Host Sports Events

Sports can be a fun way for kids to stay active. However, some kids don't have the interest or time to dedicate to being on a sports team. That's why it's a good idea for schools to host sporting events beyond their normal sports games. For example, you could host a fun run, a sack race or an obstacle course for students to participate in. and also form recreational sports teams.

Conclusion

A high-quality program about physical education in India enables all students to enjoy and succeed in many kinds of physical activities. The importance of physical education programs is to help students to develop a wide range of skills as well as gives them the ability to use tactics, strategies, and newer ideas to perform successfully both at home and school. Physical fitness is the key ingredient for a healthy lifestyle. This is why physical education is an important element in most schools. When students have regular fitness activities as part of their daily regimen, they stay fit and healthy. Regular physical activities daily help in better absorption of nutrients in the body and also helps in improving cardiovascular health and developing muscular strength. Most physical activities that students do in schools are related to higher levels of concentration which in turn help with better behaviors. Physical activities and sports activities help in boosting the knowledge learned in the classroom.

References

- [1] <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/10-benefits-of-physical-activity-for-students-301414560.html>
- [2] <https://www.sudhirmemorialinstituteliluah.com/importance-exercise-students-life>
- [3] <https://playpowercanada.ca/blog/how-to-promote-physical-activity-at-your-school/>
- [4] https://www.physio-pedia.com/Physical_Fitness_and_Its_Components https://www.physio-pedia.com/Physical_Fitness_and_Its_Components
- [5] <https://www.credencehighschool.com/blog/importance-of-physical-fitness-in-student%E2%80%99s-life>

THEMATIC STUDY ON THE MANDATORY OF YOGA AND SPORTS

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Abstract

The majority of the poses in this essay, which focuses on the "Thematic study on the mandatory of yoga and the sports performance," are not aerobic in nature, but they do still send oxygen to the body's cells through sustained stretching and contraction of various muscle groups and conscious deep breathing. Most sports increase muscular strength and endurance, frequently in particular body parts. To practise the necessary talent, a significant amount of time, effort, and dedication are needed. Another crucial factor is the body's flexibility, strength, and control. Performance will suffer if the body cannot be moved with the required grace, velocity, and speed. Everyone can benefit from yoga, but athletes especially.

Keywords: *Yoga, Injury, Fitness, Performance*

Introduction

Yoga originated thousands of years ago in India as a technique to help people achieve spiritual enlightenment. Based on the idea that the mind and body are one, students believe that Yoga improves health by improving how you see the world, which calms the spirit and decreases stress. Today, people practice Yoga to improve their physical, mental and/or spiritual wellbeing. There are many disciplines of yoga that emphasize different aspects of the mind, body and spirit. Yoga focuses largely on the physical practice, primarily Hatha Yoga. Hatha is a widespread style that incorporates a series of poses (called Asanas) that emphasize stretching, breathing (called Pranayams), relaxation and meditation techniques to help build strength, increase flexibility and balance, and improve coordination. Yoga has a lot of definitions floating around in today's world; however, if we go back to the roots of the word, we find that the term 'Yoga' has its origins in Sanskrit. It means to unite – Yoga helps the body to unite with the other vital metaphysical aspects of the mind and spirit. It is also often defined as a lifestyle which aims to have a healthy mind within a healthy body. There is a great need of yoga and yogic practices to be taught and also to practice yoga, to overcome. Physical, mental and physiological problems. My paper aims to the largely deals with the mental aspects, as it is the current need. Regular practice of asana, pranayama and meditation can help such diverse ailments such as diabetes; Yoga aims to calm and compose our minds and help us focus clearly on what really matters – good health and the happiness that accompanies it. The practice of yoga was first developed in India and has evolved over thousands of years. Yoga disciples use poses, or asana, to prepare their bodies for meditation practice—much as an athlete would prepare for a sports competition. The poses also serve as a means to alter one's consciousness and mental focus in the spiritual quest for "enlightenment." In essence, yoga is designed to bring body, mind and spirit into balance. Balancing the mind, body and spirit is a primary philosophical principle of yoga. It is considered the true way to honor the body. Yoga is an appropriate practice for many athletes, providing physical exercise, breath control and flexibility, as well as mental focus it helps athletes gain knowledge about the mind and body connection, improving body awareness and enhancing mental clarity.

Benefits of Yoga on Sports Performance

Mental health: Let us first begin with the benefits of Yoga on mental health. After all, good mental health is of paramount importance for being healthy physically as well. As advised above, breathing technique forms an integral part of Yoga. Do I hear you asking 'how?' It really is very basic by breathing deep and right, something that you would be doing when you practice Yoga, you are inhaling more oxygen and allowing the cells of your body to have access to that oxygen for a longer period of time. A common practice in yoga is to breathe only from one nostril at a time, while holding the other one closed with the tip of your finger. Medical research has shown that this boosts increased activity of the opposite side of the brain, leading to better cognitive performance and tasks associated with the other side of the brain.

Strength: Ever wondered, why so many of us, after a hard day's work, come and plunk ourselves, on our home sofas, with very little energy to even fetch a glass of water for ourselves. This is caused by lack of inner strength. Certain asanas of the yoga help generate inner strength. Inner strength is essential in doing day to day activities and in preventing you from injuries. This is especially useful, as we grow old and need more energy and strength to do the same activity.

Cardiovascular: Yoga has a lot of positive effects on the cardiovascular system of our body. A

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healthy cardiovascular system is responsible for preventing heart attacks, strokes and hypertension. Heart disease is a problem which has roots in an improper lifestyle, faulty diet and negative thinking. Our thoughts, emotions and feelings affect our body and negative emotions/thoughts send a series of complex and unhealthy chemical processes throughout the body, giving alarms that something is amiss. Yoga tends to control these by bringing in fresh life-giving oxygen. The antioxidant properties of Yoga help in preventing the negative emotions and promote a general well-being in the body.

Effects of Yoga on Different Factors Physical Effects

- 1) Increase suppleness through stretching muscles
- 2) Improves joint mobility by lengthening ligaments to their healthy limits
- 3) Reduces risk of injury and assists with injury rehabilitation
- 4) Effective as a form of soft tissue and collagen fiber rehabilitation
- 5) Helps to bring the body back into alignment and improves posture
- 6) Increases stride length
- 7) Enhances co-ordination and agility
- 8) Contributes to improved cardiovascular fitness and stamina
- 9) Teaches athletes how the body performs and functions as a synergistic unit
- 10) Lowers resting heart rate and increases vo2 max.

Psychological Effects

- 1) Relieves performance anxiety and stress, and frees athletes from mental distractions
- 2) Develops determination and self-discipline
- 3) Teaches athletes to challenge themselves and go outside of their comfort zone
- 4) Reduces stress and provides a method of relaxation
- 5) Breath work provides athlete with techniques they can use whilst competing to control arousal levels
- 6) Helps athletes to achieve flow and get in 'the zone'
- 7) Teaches athletes how to use imagery and relaxation
- 8) Helps athletes to understand the importance of relaxing, resting, and recovering

Team Effects

- 1) Improves team cohesion
- 2) Increases team motivation
- 3) Provides an opportunity for team unity outside the demands of intense training
- 4) Increases trust
- 5) Improves player-player support

Conclusion

Overall, the studies comparing Thematic study on the Requisite of yoga and the sports performance and exercise seem to indicate that, in both healthy and diseased populations, yoga may be as effective as or better than exercise at improving a variety of health-related outcome measures including HRV, to improve subjective measures of fatigue pain, and sleep in healthy and ill populations. However, future clinical trials are needed to further examine the distinctions between exercise and yoga, particularly how the two modalities may differ. In their, thematic study on Requisite of yoga and the sports performance. Researcher find out that yoga in sports as important as other think it helps us in different ways and different levels in sports mean life.

References

- [1] Gokal R, Shillito L. Positive impact of yoga and pranayama on obesity, hypertension, blood sugar, and cholesterol: A pilot assessment. *J Altern Complement Med* 2007; 13:1056–1057.
- [2] Khatri D, Mathur KC, Gahlot S et al. Effects of yoga and meditation on clinical and biochemical parameters of meta-bolic syndrome. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2007; 78:e9–e10.
- [3] Michalsen A, Grossman P, Acil A et al. Rapid stress reduction and anxiolysis among
- [4] distressed women as a consequence of a three month intensive yoga program. *Med Sci Monit* 2005; 11:555–561.
- [5] Selvamurthy W, Sridharan K, Ray US et al. A new physiological approach to control essential hypertension. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol* 1998; 42:205–213.
- [6] West J, Otter C, Geher K, Johnson J et al. Effects of Hatha yoga and African dance on perceived stress, affect, and salivary cortisol. *Ann Behav Med* 2004; 28:114–118.

TEACHING COMPETENCY IN MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The process of teaching learning is as old as human being on earth. It has been carried out by human beings and even by animals to teach their young ones for successful adjustments in the environment. The process has undergone several changes from non-formal to formal with the help of passage of time.

Introduction

Education has been playing a crucial role in bringing about transformation in the social, cultural, technological and scientific advances which are linked with human progress. It is in this frame of reference that under the impact of globalization it has been widely organized as a catalyst for change. In the 21st century world we are rapidly moving towards this realization insofar as the subtler progresses of influencing the mindset of our new generation is concerned.

Role of Curriculum in Teacher Education

Curriculum of human rights education should incorporate both knowledge of rational ideas related to human rights and moral and human values concerning human rights in terms of the changing perspectives. The evolution of the concept of human rights and its articulation in different forms must be included in the content of human rights education. In addition, the mechanisms created at the international and national level for the protection of human rights especially in the wake of globalization should also form part of the curriculum of human rights education.

Teacher Preparation

The profile of a teacher who inspires students to respect and observe rights of others and adhere to human duties towards fellow beings is characterized by many attributes. For example, such a teacher follows progressive and humane approach towards issues and problems, affords equal opportunity to all students.

Role of Teachers

Teachers send powerful messages to students through what they do in the classroom and the kinds of discussions they will and will not engage in. So if we educate teachers to incorporate explicitly and examine values and morals at every level, it would enable them to see that everything they do in the classroom provides an opportunity for the modeling of values making an examination of one's own values and morals and how to develop morals and values in others central to education may enable teachers to be the powerful agents of change that they hope to be for their students.

Teachers Role in Perception

The teacher has been recognized as the key person in the preservation, progression and projection of a nation's cultural heritage. The teacher is supposed to be the role model for the wards put to his charge as also the society as a whole. Teacher is one through whom the new generation is prepared to lead a good life in the society and the environment to which it belongs. Teachers have a great role to play in shaping the mind and heart of the youth so that they may prepare themselves as an upcoming generation of good citizens of a democracy. The profession of the teacher should not be reduced to a trade, it should be confined to keep burning the lamp of the civilization.

Teaching as a Profession

A professional is one who is able to acquire a fund of knowledge, range of skills and their application in the service of humanity. The dictionary meanings of professional are belonging to a profession, showing the skill of a trained person doing specified work etc. for payment and not as a pastime. The criteria for an occupation to be recognized as a profession includes, among others, the following considerations.

- 1) A profession is an occupation, performing a crucial social function.
- 2) It requires considerable degree of skill.
- 3) It involves a concept of social service, though the person earns his living by virtue of one's profession.

- 4) A profession has a clearly defined membership of a professional group.
- 5) Every profession has its own code of ethics. This emerges through the thinking and consideration of service by the professionals themselves. This code is self-imposed.

Teachers Professional Ethics

In Indian society, teacher is traditionally given a very high, status is accorded due regard and respect and in sometimes worshipped also. Hence an extremely high conduct and behaviour pattern is expected of him. Professional ethics makes explicit the teacher's role and defines his rights and duties along with the knowledge of what is involved in his virtuous conduct. In the case of teaching profession, the dimensions of ethics extend from the description of an ideal personality of the teacher to the teacher's desire, wishes and aspirations, to his role in social welfare and uplift of the pupil's individuality and encouragement of an ideal conduct in him.

Teacher's Never-Ending Efforts

The content of teacher education needs to be in conformity with the changing educational and social needs of a given society. The teacher can improve his professionalism in the following ways: Through participation in-

- 1) Pre-service and induction programmes.
- 2) Courses and workshops on teaching techniques.
- 3) Workshops on assessment techniques.
- 4) Consultancy services to individual staff.
- 5) Identifying effective classroom teachers.
- 6) Posting opportunity for other teachers to observe them in action.

Moral Obligations for Teachers

The teachers moral obligation is to provide excellent instruction. Teachers with a high level of moral professionalism have a deep obligation to help students learn. Teachers with that sense of obligation naturally tend to demonstrate their moral professionalism by-

- 1) Coming to work regularly and on time.
- 2) Being well-informed about their subject matter.
- 3) Regularly reviewing and updating instructional practices.
- 4) Cooperating and, if necessary, confronting parents of under-achieving students.
- 5) Cooperating with colleagues and observing school policies for effective work production from the whole group.
- 6) Proposing constructive movements and firmly rejecting or criticizing unsatisfactory policies.

Multiple Intelligence

In present study, multiple intelligence is the set of skills allowing individuals to find and resolve genuine problems they face at their environment by perceiving and understanding through; verbal, logical, spatial, musical, kinesthetic, naturalistic, existential, interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence.

ICT Awareness

In present study, ICT awareness refers to Information Communication Technological awareness about technical and technological skills of utilizing electronic devices by browsing, designing, communicating and maintenance of hardware and software.

Conclusion

The teacher is the most important factor for the success of an educational programme. The school may have excellent building, well-designed curricula, good teaching aids but if the teachers are not efficient, educational programme can never be successful. No system of education, no syllabus, no methodology and no textbook can rise above the level of the teachers. If a nation wants quality education as well as a value-oriented society, it must have quality teachers.

References

- [1] Ahmad Samir Nain (2007) Human Rights and Globalization www.countercurrents.org.
- [2] Chitkara MG (1996) Human Rights Commitment and Betrayal, A.PH Publishing. New Delhi.
- [3] Kothari, D.S. (1966) (Chairman) Education Commission (1964-66). Ministry of Education, Govt of India, New Delhi.
- [4] Mudaliar, A.L. (1953) (Chairman) Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) Ministry of Education, Govt. of India, New Delhi.
- [5] Education, Govt. of India, New Delhi.

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EXERCISE PROTOCOL FOR PREDICTING THE SENSITIVE ZONE ON HEART RATE

MAXIMUM AMONG UNTRAINED SCHOOL BOYS.

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Introduction

Physiology: Study of functioning of living organisms or their constituent tissues or cells. Heart Rate: The number of times the heart contracts per minute to pump blood around the body.

Aim

The purpose of the study is to determine the significant change in Heart Rate max. Capacity of untrained The Hyderabad Public School, Begumpet, in the age group of 12-14 years.

Significance of the Study

- 1) The study will help to estimate the significant change in Heart Rate maximum.
- 2) This will also help to find out the intensity of the exercise (or) training sensitive zone to improve Heart Rate maximum.
- 3) This study may help the physical education teachers, coaches and other related physical educational professionals dealing with the children on sports, fitness etc.
- 4) This research may also help in bringing new scope relating to Heart Rate maximum.

Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that Medium intensity duration exercise brings a significant change in Heart Rate max. Capacity in the children.

Delimitations

- 1) This study is delimited to the Students between the age group of 12-14 year Boys of The Hyderabad Public School, Begumpet Region only.
- 2) All the Students selected for this study were not trained in the past. Limitation: factors like socio economic status, daily routine life style and food habits of the subjects which may have an influence on the Heart Rate max. Capacity of the children could not be controlled.

Methodology

The purpose of this study was to compare the Heart Rate Max. among untrained school children of The Hyderabad Public School, Begumpet. To achieve this purpose, 90 students were selected randomly and were categorized in three different groups, i.e. high intensity group, middle intensity group and low intensity group as random samples. They ranged in age between fourteen to sixteen years only. The test is more economical in terms of space and the time aspects.

Experimental Variables

Harvard Step of 13 inches height for higher grouped students 2. Harvard Step of 9 inches height for middle grouped students 3. Harvard Step of 4 inches height for lower grouped students

Statistical Techniques

$$\sum x \quad M = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Mean, Where M = mean = sum of scores x = raw score N = Total number of scores

Analysis of Data and Results of Study

Heart (Final) Rate	N	Mean	Std Dev	Standard Error
4 benchers inches	30	126.2222	12.81244	2.33922
9 benchers inches	30	150.5295	4.93529	.90106
13 benchers inches	30	147.3907	9.72754	1.77600
Total	90	141.3808	14.49490	1.52790

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Conclusions

- 1) Based on the results of the above study the investigator has drawn the following conclusions:
- 2) Among these three groups 9 inches medium group have better average compared to 13 inches High bench and 4 inches Low bench group Girls.
- 3) This says that the 9 inches Medium bench test improves the Heart Rate Max. among the untrained school Boys between the age group of 12 to 14 years.

Recommendations

In the light of the facts presented above the investigator has made the following recommendations. All coaches who are giving training in improving Heart Rate Max must be specialized in their own field so that the best learning can be made possible among the participants' Good scientific and systematic coaching help the players to achieve the high level of sport performance. Educational institutions are the main agencies to promote players since childhood educational institutions must provide adequate facilities to the Boys to become fair by taking part in various physical activities.

References

- [1] Adoims C. Willan, "Foundation of Physical Education and Sports Science", Philadelphia, Lea and Feliger, 1979, P.232. Bucher A. Charles A, "Foundation of Physical Education and Sports" ST. Louis, Missouri, C.V. Mosby Company, 1983, P.143 Clark H. Harrison and David H Clark, "Research Process in Physical Education", New Jersey, Prentice Hall Inc. Engle Wood Cliffs, 1984, P.203.
- [2] Clark H. Harrison "Physical Fitness Practices and Programmes for Elementary and Secondary Schools" "Physical Fitness Research Digest" (Resident Council on Physical Fitness and Sports" Oct. 1976) P.1 Corrol V. Victor, "AAPHER Youth Fitness test TEST s and maximum oxygen uptake" (Coctroral Dissertation, University of Illionis 1967).
- [3] Curetion T.K. Flexibility as an aspect of physical fitness, "Research Quarterly Supplement", 12 May 1942, P. 381-390.
- [4] Golya J Armed and Millar Earl, "Interpreting Education Research", (OOWA, WMC, Borwn Company) 1970, P.16

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EFFECT OF MEDITATIONAL PRACTICES ON ANXIETY, PERCEPTION, REACTION TIME AND MOVEMENT TIME AMONG WOMEN ATHLETES OF TELANGANA GOVERNMENT DEGREE COLLEGES.

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Significance of the Study

Sports, physical education experts and sports scientists are continuously evaluating the sports performance in relation to the physical physiological technical, tactical, psychological and other medical components on various factors. They try to discover these factors and to contribute for the elite sports performance to enable to find and utilize the practical aspects of now nourishing the sports persons. The significance of this study is to inculcate the importance of meditational practices on selected personality traits of Women athlete's performance of Telangana Government Degree colleges.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of meditational practices on the following selected personality traits.

- 1) It there is any relation between meditational practices on anxiety and performance among athletes in relation to age, sex and discipline.
- 2) To identify whether there is any relation between meditational practices on perception and performance among athletes according to age, sex and discipline.
- 3) It there is any relation between meditational practices on Reaction Time and performance among athletes in relation to age, sex and discipline
- 4) To identify whether there is any relation between meditational practices on Movement Time and performance among athletes according to age, sex and discipline.

Objectives of the Study

To find out the impact of meditational practices on selected personality traits viz – anxiety, perception, Reaction Time and Movement Time among women Athletes of Telangana Degree colleges.

Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that there may be significant association and effect of meditational practices in relation to performance on selected personality traits viz anxiety, perception, reaction time and movement time among women athletes of telangana government degree colleges.

- 1) Hypothesis – I: There may not be any significant effect of Meditation on Anxiety of Control Group
- 2) Hypothesis – II: There may not be any significant effect of Meditation on Anxiety of Experimental Group.
- 3) Hypothesis – III: Comparison of Anxiety among Pre-Test and Post-Test score differences between Control Group and Experimental Group of WOMEN ATHLETES OF
- 4) TELANGANA GOVERNMENT DEGREE COLLEGES.
- 5) Hypothesis – IV: There may not be any significant effect of Meditation on Depth Perception of Control Group.
- 6) Hypothesis – V: There may not be any significant effect of Meditation on Depth Perception of Experimental Group.
- 7) Hypothesis – VI: Comparison of Depth Perception among Pre-Test and Post-Test score differences between Control Group and Experimental Group of WOMEN ATHLETES OF
- 8) Telangana government degree colleges.
- 9) Hypothesis – VII: there may not be any significant effect of meditation on reaction time of control group.
- 10) Hypothesis –VIII: there may not be any significant effect of meditation on reaction time of experimental group.
- 11) Hypothesis – IX: comparison of reaction time among pre-test and post-test score differences between control group and experimental group of women athletes of Telangana government degree colleges.

Delimitations

The study is delimited to meditational practices on selected personality traits viz anxiety, perception, Reaction Time, Movement Time and performance of women athletes of Talangana Government Degree

Colleges, in relation to age, sex and discipline.

Limitations

The study is limited to the following aspects. The factors like climatic conditions and life style will be beyond the control of the investigator. The physiological factors of the sample will not be considered.

Operational Definitions

- 1) Sports
- 2) Yoga
- 3) Asana
- 4) Psychology
- 5) Sports Psychology
- 6) Anxiety
- 7) Perception
- 8) Reaction Time
- 9) Movement Time
- 10) Meditation
- 11) Personality Traits

Methodology Design of the Study

The schematic presentation of the design of the study is presented here under. The purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of meditational practices on selected personality traits - Anxiety, Perception, Reaction Time, and Movement time of athletes of Telangana degree colleges. The study was formulated based on the simple random sampling. The samples were collected from the 80 athletes studying in government degree colleges of Telangana state in the age group of 18 to 21 years. These sample were randomly selected the women athletes of government degree college of Telangana state. The group is divided into control and experiment groups. The experiment will last for 6 weeks, there will be one session everyday of 1 hour each for athletes of experimental group. the control group is not allowed to participate in any meditational practices except their routine sports training schedule. data for selected variables may be collected at the beginning by conducting pre-test and after 6 weeks by conducting post test the test results may be analyzed with evaluation.

Stage1: Pre- test. Stage2:experimentprogramme. Stage3: post test

Tools Used

To measure anxiety SCAT test (sports competition anxiety test) may be used. Tester's competency. To measure the Anxiety the (SCAT) by Rainer Maxtens, Dinne Gill, Tara Scanlan and sport Competition Anxiety test, To measure perception the depth perception test was used the SCAT questionnaire was designed in the following pattern. To measure perception, Depth perception test was used. Movement time test: Name of the test: - nelson speed of movement time. Purpose of the test: to measure the speed of movement of the athlete. Reaction time test: Name of the test: reaction time. Purpose of the test: - To measure the Reaction time [visual and auditory] of the Athletes.

Statistical Techniques Used

The data collected in this study was subjected to statistical analysis with appropriate tools. The descriptive statistics was used to find out the mean, standard deviation and t – test f - test was computed. For graphical presentation excel package of MS-office was used for better compliance.

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TRAININGS ON SPEED AND DRIBBLING PERFORMANCE AMONG INTER COLLEGIATE HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of different trainings on speed and dribbling performance among intercollegiate Hockey players. To achieve the purpose of the study, 30 male Hockey players were randomly selected as participants from Bharathidasan University affiliated colleges. The selected participants were divided into three groups such as Group I underwent weight training (n=10), Group II underwent plyometric training (n=10) and Group III underwent combined training (n=10). The experimental groups I, II & III were subjected to eight weeks weight training, plyometric training, and combined training respectively. The training was given 3 days per week on alternate days every training session lasted for 45 to 60 minutes in addition to their regular training programme. The participants of all groups were tested on Speed and dribbling prior to and after the training period. The data were collected by administering 50 Meters Run for Speed and Johnson Hockey skill test for dribbling. The pre-test data were collected two days before the training program and the post-test data were collected two days after the training program. The data collected from pre-test and post-test experimentation on Speed and dribbling before and after the training period and statistically analyzed by using dependent 't' test and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to find out significant difference if any between the experimental group. It was concluded that, there was a significant improvement and significant difference exist due to the effect of weight training, plyometric training and combined training on speed and dribbling performance among intercollegiate Hockey players.

Keywords: *Plyometrics And Combined Training*

Introduction

Hockey players move with great speed over a limited space. It is one of the most vigorous games and requires a great variety of athletic traits. In the game of Hockey all the movements are involved like passing, throwing, changing the direction quickly, and sudden stop, jumping for rebound, feinting, maneuvering the opponent while going for offensive move and guarding the opponents in the defensive. All these require rapid movements demanding frequent changes in direction. For one to respond to such situation a player should possess good motor fitness, physiological and psychological qualities. Hockey is a highly competitive game and it demands high physical qualities. The prime physical qualities are explosive strength, strength endurance, agility, speed, various coordinative abilities etc. Height without fitness or technical ability without endurance becomes a liability. In all court games, including Hockey, fast starts, sudden stops, and quick change in direction are basic to good performance (Griffith and Sian, 2011). Speed is the ability to achieve high velocity. It is a manifestation of explosive force applied to a specific task but is often incorrectly perceived as independent from (or incompatible with) strength. Functional motor skill requiring accelerate as well as declarative speed strength (Bacechle and Earle, 2000). Dribbling is the act of bouncing the ball continuously with one hand, and to move the ball around the court of opponent is a requirement for a player to take steps with the ball. For that, purpose the players required speed quality to tackle the ball and move around the court. Good ball handlers frequently dribble and move fast and switch directions suddenly, making a less predictable dribbling pattern that is more difficult to defend against. Weight training is used to develop strength of specific areas of the body. It is used to develop muscular strength and power. It also develops muscular endurance, elasticity and coordination. The primary objective of weight training is not to learn to lift as much as weight as possible, but to increase strength and power for application to some other sports.

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study, 30 male Hockey players were randomly selected as participants from Bharathidasan University affiliated colleges. The selected participants were divided into three groups such as Group I underwent weight training (n=10), Group II underwent plyometric training (n=10) and Group III underwent combined training (n=10). The experimental groups I, II & III were subjected to eight weeks weight training, plyometric training, and combined training respectively. The training was given 3 days per week on alternate days every training session lasted for 45 to 60 minutes in addition to their regular training programme. The participants of all groups were tested on Speed and dribbling prior to and after the training period. The data were collected by administering 50 Meters Run for Speed and Johnson Hockey skill test for dribbling. The pre-test data were collected two days before the training program and the post-test data were

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collected two days after the training program. The data collected from pre-test and post-test experimentation on Speed and dribbling before and after the training period and statistically analyzed by using dependent 't' test and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to find out significant difference if any between the experimental group.

Results and Discussions

Table – I: Mean and Paired Sample 't' Test of Weight Plyometric and Combined Training Group on Selected Dependent Variables

Name of training groups	Name of dependent variables	Pre test mean	Post testmean	't'
Weight	Speed	6.66	6.41	3.10*
	Dribbling	14.80	19.80	10.11*
Plyometric	Speed	6.83	6.34	10.17*
	Dribbling	15.2	22.80	8.04*
Combined	Speed	6.70	15.20	13.12*
	Dribbling	6.12	25.40	12.98*

*Significant of 0.05 level

Table value for level of significant df 9 was 2.262. The paired sample 't' was compute on selected dependent variables. The results were presented in the above Table I. All the 't' values are significantly higher than the required table value of df 9 at 0.05 level of confidence was 2.262. The result of the study shows that the weight training, plyometric training and combined (weight and plyometrics) training group significantly improved the performance of all the selected dependent variables. The results of the study shows that selected dependent variables speed and dribbling performance significantly improve due to the eight week weight training, plyometric training and combined (weight and plyometrics) training program.

Speed

Table II Presents the results of the ANCOVA for weight training, plyometric training and combined (weight and plyometric) training on Selected dependent variables.

Table – II Analysis of Covariance Computed for Weight Training Plyometric Training and Combined Training for Selected Dependent Variables

VARIABLES	SOURCE	SS	df	MS	F
Speed	Groups	0.504	2	0.252	8.14*
	Error	0.806	26	0.031	
Dribbling	Groups	144.324	2	72.162	15.80*
	Error	118.774	26	4.568	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence Table value required for significance at 0.05 level of 2 & 26 was 3.37. One way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was computed for the dependent variable Speed and dribbling. The independent variables included three training groups, weight training, plyometric training and combined training. The dependent variable was speed and dribbling, the covariate was an initial performance of the 50 meters run and Johnson Hockey skill test for dribbling. The ANCOVA 'F' ratio was significant for df (2, 26) = 8.14, p < 0.05 (See Table II) for speed and The ANCOVA 'F' ratio was significant for df (2, 26) = 15.80, p < 0.05 (See Table II) for dribbling. In order to find out which of the paired means significantly differ scheffe's post hoc test is applied and present in the Table III for three training groups.

Table – III Scheffe's post hoc paired means comparisons on speed of experimental groups

Group	Adjusted mean	Adjusted mean differences			
		1	2	3	4
Weight	6.458	----			
Plyometric	6.271	0.19	----		
Combined	6.141	0.32*	0.13	----	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence Scheffe's C.I value 0.31;

Follow-up was conducted to evaluate pairwise differences among the adjusted means for

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experimental groups. The results showed that combined training group (M = 6.141) had significantly better than the plyometric training group (M = 6.271) and weight training group (M = 6.458). Combined training group had better performance over the plyometric training and weight training group. Combined training group and Weight training group shows significant differences on speed performance, combined training group and Plyometric training group do not show any significant differences on speed performance.

Dribbling

One way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was computed for the dependent variable dribbling. The independent variables included three training groups, weight training, plyometric training and combined training. The dependent variable was Dribbling and the covariate was an initial performance of the Johnson Hockey skill Test. The ANCOVA 'F' ratio was significant for $df(2, 26) = 15.80$, $p < 0.05$ (See Table II). In order to find out which of the paired means significantly differ Scheffe's post hoc test is applied and present in the Table IV for three training groups.

Table – IV Scheffe's post hoc paired means comparisons on dribbling of experimental groups

Group	Adjusted mean	Adjusted mean differences			
		1	2	3	4
Weight	19.944	----			
Plyometric	22.728	2.78	----		
Combined	25.328	5.38*	2.60	----	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence Scheffe's C.I value 2.88

Follow-up was conducted to evaluate pairwise differences among the adjusted means for experimental groups. The results showed that combined training group (M = 25.328) had significantly better than the plyometric training group (M = 22.728) and weight training group (M = 19.944). Combined training group had better performance over the plyometric training group and weight training group. Combined training group and Weight training group shows significant differences on speed performance, combined training group and Plyometric training group do not show any significant differences on Dribbling performance.

Conclusions

There was significant improvement in weight training, plyometric training and combined training group participants in speed and dribbling performance. The experimental groups namely weight training, plyometric training and combined training groups had significant difference towards improving the participants speed and dribbling performance. Combined training group and weight training group shows significant differences improving the speed and dribbling performance. Combined training group and plyometric training group did not show any significant differences improving the speed and dribbling performance.

Reference

- [1] Bacechle, Thomas R., and Earle, Roger, W. (Eds). (2000) Essentials of Strength Training and Conditioning (2nd ed). In chapter-20, Speed Agility and Speed Endurance Development by Steven S.Plisk. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- [2] Adams, K, O'Shea, JP, O'Shea, KL, and Climstein, M. (1992) The effect of six weeks of squat, plyometric and squat-plyometric training on power production. The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research, 6, 36–41.
- [3] Delamarche P., Gratas A., Beillot J., Dassonville J., Rochcongar P., Lessard Y.(1987). Extent of lactic anaerobic metabolism in Handballers. Int. Journal Sports Medicine. 8:55-59.
- [4] Griffiths, Sian (2011). "The Canadian who invented Hockey". BBC News. Retrieved September 14.
- [5] Shallaby, H. K. (2010). The Effect of Plyometric Exercises Use on the Physical and Skillful Performance of Hockey Players. World Journal of Sport Sciences, 3(4), 316- 324.

INFLUENCE OF CIRCUIT TRAINING ON SELECTED PHYSICAL FITNESS VARIABLES AMONG MEN HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out the influence of circuit training on selected physical fitness variables among women hockey players. For the purpose of the study 30 college level men hockey players, age ranging between 17 and 25 years from were selected as subjects from American College, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India. They were further divided into experimental and control group randomly after the preliminary tests taken for the study. All students in this institution had identical and controlled living condition with variation in socio-economic background. The investigator was well acquainted with the subjects being a student himself in the same institution. This institution being a fully residential institution this study was planned out as they could be taken into confidence and control. Prior to the administration of further procedures a series of meetings was held with subjects they were made clear about the objectives and purpose of the study. Testing and training procedures were also explained to them in details. They were requested to co-operate and participate actively for the same. After the pre-test condition they were randomly distributed to experimental and control group of fifteen each. The study was formulated as a true random group design, consisting of a pre-test and post-test. The subjects (n=30) were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen men students each. The groups were assigned as experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) in an equivalent manner. The experimental group participated in the circuit training for a period of six weeks.

Keywords: *Circuit Training, Women, Hockey, Agility, Speed, Explosive Strength.*

Introduction

Circuit training was invented in 1953 as an efficient way for coaches to train many athletes in a limited amount of time with limited equipment. Circuit training is an effective organisational form of doing physical exercises for improving all physical fitness components. Hockey is the fastest and most beautiful of ball games. Though it was introduced into the sub-continent by the British, Indians have developed their own style game. The name „Hockey’ was perhaps derived from a French word ‘Hoguet’ which means shepherds’ scrook. whatever be the game’s ancient origin Hockey as we it to-day, originated in the British Isle. The Birth of modern hockey dates from 1876, when a few clubs joined together and formed a hockey union for drafting suitable rules. The hockey association was formed in 1886. In 1900 the international Hockey Board was formed and its rules are universally adopted for men’s Hockey. Since 1886 the game has spread to all parts of the world and is increasing in popularity day by day. The game Hockey was introduced in India by British military officers for the soldiers and it was spreadover to the civilians.

Methodology

The purpose of this study was to find out the influence of circuit training on selected physical fitness variables among women hockey players. For the purpose of the study 30 college level men hockey players, age ranging between 17 and 25 years from were selected as subjects from American College, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India. They were further divided into experimental and control group randomly after the preliminary tests taken for the study. All students in this institution had identical and controlled living condition with variation in socio-economic background. The investigator was well acquainted with the subjects being a student himself in the same institution. This institution being a fully residential institution this study was planned out as they could be taken into confidence and control. Prior to the administration of further procedures a series of meetings was held with subjects they were made clear about the objectives and purpose of the study. Testing and training procedures were also explained to them in details. They were requested to co-operate and participate actively for the same. After the pre-test condition they were randomly distributed to experimental and control group of fifteen each. The study was formulated as a true random group design, consisting of a pre-test and post-test. The subjects (n=30) were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen men students each. The groups were assigned as experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) in an equivalent manner. The experimental group participated in the circuit training for a period of six weeks.

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Results and Discussions

The data collected prior to and after the experimental periods on circuit training group and control group were analysed and presented in the following table - I.

Table-I Descriptive Analysis of Pre and Post Test Means of Experimental and Control Group on Selected Fitness Variables

S.No	Variables	Pre Test Mean	Post Test Mean
1	Speed	Exp:7.56	Exp:7.13
		Con:7.73	Con:7.56
2	Agility	Exp:11.73	Exp:9.49
		Con:11.20	Con:10.30

Table II. Computation of t^{**} ratio between the pre-test and post-test means of speed of experimental and control group S. No Variables Mean diff SD σ DM 't' ratio
 1 Speed Exp: 0.44 Exp: 0.39 Exp:0.10 4.34* Con:0.16
 Con:0.32 Con:0.08 1.97

s.no	Variables	Mean diff	SD	σ DM	't' ratio
1.	Speed	Exp:0.44	Exp:0.39	Exp:0.10	4.34*
		Con:0.16	Con:0.32	Con:0.08	1.97

*Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table II indicates that the obtained^{**} ratio for speed of experimental group was 4.34. The obtained^{**} ratio on speed was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The obtained^{**} ratio for speed of control group was 1.97. The obtained^{**} ratio on speed was found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant.

Table III. Computation of t^{**} ratio between the pre-test and post-test means of agility of experimental and control group

s.no	Variables	Mean diff	SD	σ DM	't' ratio
1.	Agility	Exp:2.24	Exp:0.80	Exp:0.21	25.79*
		Con:0.89	Con:1.79	Con:0.46	1.94

Significant at 0.05 level

An examination of table III indicates that the obtained^{**} ratio for agility of experimental group was 25.79. The obtained^{**} ratio on agility was found to be greater than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be significant. The obtained^{**} ratios for agility of control group was 1.94. The obtained^{**} ratio on agility was found to be lesser than the required table value of 2.14 at 0.05 level of significance for 14 degrees of freedom. So it was found to be not significant.

Conclusions

Within the limitation of the present study, the following conclusions were drawn. It was observed that there was significant improvement in the speed of the experimental group owing to circuit training. It was observed that there was significant improvement in the agility of the experimental group owing to circuit training. There was no significant improvement in the selected variables of the control group.

References

- [1] Antony A. Anmarine, Developmental Conditioning for Physical Education and Athletics (St. Louis: The C.Mosby co, 1972), 9.
- [2] Arther Henry Pilch, "Cardio-vascular Responses of Selected Middle Aged Subjects to Regular Periods of Exercise", Dissertation Abstracts International, Vol. 32 (August, 1971) p. 775.
- [3] Kraimer, et al., (2001) Koffand Bauman (1997) Williams and Cash (2001) Effects of aerobic and circuit training on fitness and body image among women. Journal of Sport Behavior.
- [4] Leray Cofield "Comparison of the physical fitness level of seventh grade boys before and after a planned physical education programmer", complete research in health physical education and recreation 13, P.144).
- [5] Leshkevitch, C.C., "The Influence of Sequence of Exercise in Training Undertaking in the Development of the Physiological Foundations of Speed, Strength and Endurance of Young Sportsman", Research Quarterly, Vol: 83:2, (October 1982), p. 500.

CORRECTIVE FEEDBACK RECEIVED ON DISCOURSE PRODUCTION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE OF SECONDARY SCHOOLSTUDENTS IN KERALA

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to find out the Corrective Feedback(CF) based on form and focus received by secondary school students to their discourses produced in English Language classrooms in Kerala. The study used Normative Survey method to collect data using Corrective Feedback Frequency Scale. The sample was taken from 80 grade nine students from the State and Central Board secondary schools in Kerala. Descriptive statistics and Independent t Test was used to analyse the data collected. The results of the study show that as a whole, majority of secondary school students receive moderate corrective feedback for their discourse production in English language. The analysis of subsamples indicates that there is significant difference in the corrective feedback received by learners for their discourses in English Language in the State and Central Board secondary schools in Kerala. This research can assist instructors to get informed of feedback alternatives and their frequency of use and improve both their teaching skills and productive skills of their pupils in English language.

Keywords: *Corrective Feedback, Discourse Production, Secondary School Students, English Language*

Introduction

Corrective Feedback (CF) is used in language instruction to improve accuracy and overall quality of discourses produced by learners. CF assists learners in identifying, rectifying, and avoiding errors in their future spoken and written utterances. CF can either be in written or spoken form and is given when a learner uses the target language incorrectly. Corrective feedback, both written and spoken, often contains corrections, notes, words of encouragement or praise, guidance, and recommendations to help students to improve their discourses. Teachers of English as a second language employ many types of corrective feedback techniques to help students improve their productive skills in English language. Based on the style of delivering feedback, it can be direct, indirect or a combination of both. In case of direct CF, teachers explicitly correct the students by supplying the correct form to the students whereas indirect CF types only mentions that there are some inaccuracies in the discourse which needs the attention of the learner. Considering the focus of the feedback given, it is classified as Focused CF and Unfocused CF. While using Focused feedback technique, an instructor attempts to correct only a limited type of errors, rather than correcting all types of errors present in the discourse. When each and every error is given feedback, it falls into the category of Unfocused feedback. Corrective feedback enhances the accuracy, clarity and precision of spoken and written discourses in English language by learners (Rouhi & Mohebbi, 2020). Corrective feedback encourages learners to perceive errors as opportunities for growth, that aids their learning and motivation. Teachers, using corrective feedback, provides a sense of direction to learners and stimulate their thought process in order to promote the independence of learners. ESL teachers use a variety of corrective feedback strategies to assist their learners in developing their productive skills in English as a second language. Considering its importance in second language learning and acquisition, the present study attempts to find out the frequency of CF received by secondary school students as part of teaching and learning of English Language in Schools in Kerala.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out whether Corrective Feedback is received on discourses in English language by secondary school students in Kerala.
- 2) To find out whether there is significant difference in the Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English language by secondary school students with respect to type of management.

Hypotheses Formulated for the Study

- 1) Secondary school students in Kerala will receive Corrective Feedback in different frequencies to their discourses in English Language.
- 2) There is significant difference in the mean scores of Corrective feedback received on discourses in English language by secondary school students studying in the government and Central Board of Secondary Education Schools.

Methodology

The present study adopted Normative Survey method for the study. The population of the study

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consists of secondary school students studying in schools following state and Central Board syllabuses in Kerala. The sample selected for the study was 80 ninth graders in the government and Central Board of Secondary Education Schools in Kerala. The sampling method used is simple random sampling. Corrective Feedback Scale was used to collect data from the participants. Descriptive Statistics and Independent t Test are used to interpret data for the present study.

Corrective Feedback Scale

Corrective Feedback Scale with 15 items was prepared by the investigator for assessing the frequency of corrective feedback received by participants for discourse production. The 15 items are broken down into three categories based on their form and focus viz. Written or oral, Direct or Indirect and Focused or Unfocused. The tool is a 5-point scale with the options Never (1), Rarely (2), Sometimes (3), Very often (4), and Always (5). The components of the scale are designed as;

- 1) Items 1, 4, 5, 9, 14, and – Written or Oral CF Items
- 2) Items 2, 8, 10, 13, 15. – Direct or Indirect CF Items and
- 3) Items 3, 6, 7, 11, 12, – Focused or Unfocused CF Items.
- 4) Items 2, 4, 5, 7, 8 are reverse-scored.

Analysis and Interpretation

The purpose of this study is to find out the Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language of learners in Secondary schools in Kerala. The investigator examined the hypotheses formulated for the study using Descriptive Statistics and Independent t Test. Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language was analysed and the details are presented in Table 1. The calculated mean value for the Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language is 52.09 and standard deviation is 13.45. The secondary school students who scored greater than 65.54 (i.e., Mean + Standard Deviation) have received high frequency of Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language and those who scored less than 38.64 (i.e., Mean – Standard Deviation) have received low frequency of Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language. The secondary school students who scored between 38.64 and 65.54 have received moderate frequency of Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English Language.

Table 1 Analysis of the Corrective Feedback Received on Discourses of Secondary School Students

Frequency of Corrective Feedback	Students	Percentage
High	20	25
Moderate	46	58
Low	14	17

From table 1, it is clear that 58% of secondary school students receive moderate frequency of Corrective Feedback, 25 % receive high frequency of Corrective Feedback and 17% receive low frequency of Corrective Feedback. Data and results of the test of significance of difference in the mean scores of the corrective feedback received on discourses of secondary school students based on type of management. Analysis on the Corrective Feedback received on discourses of secondary school students based on type of management is analyzed by the investigator and presented in table 2.

Table 2 Data and Results of the Test of Significance of Differences in the Mean Scores of the Corrective Feedback based on type of Management

Type of Management	Frequency	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
State	43	42.23	9.89		
Central	37	63.47	5.86	1.99	0.05

From table 2, it is found that the mean score and standard deviation on the Corrective Feedback received on discourses of secondary school learners studying in the government schools are 42.23 and 9.89 respectively and that of the learners from Central Board Schools are 63.47 and 5.86 respectively. The critical ratio obtained is 1.99, which is greater than the table value at both 0.05 level. This showed that there is significant difference in the Corrective Feedback received on discourses of secondary school students with regards to their type of Management.

Findings of the Study

The study was conducted to find out the Corrective Feedback received on discourses in English

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Language of learners in Secondary schools in Kerala. The present study was conducted among 80 secondary school students who study in grade nine in Kerala government and Central Board of Secondary Education Schools. From the study, the investigator found that, majority of the secondary school students receive moderate frequency of Corrective Feedback to their discourse production in English language. The study also revealed that there is significant difference in the Corrective Feedback received on discourses of secondary school students based on the type of management.

Implications of the Study

The study throws light into the present status of feedback received by secondary school students on their discourses in their English language Classrooms. The study has the following implications:

- 1) Teachers of English language can plan and support students discourse production by providing right amount of feedback at the right time.
- 2) Different types of Corrective Feedback techniques are supposed to be used by teachers of English Language in their classrooms to facilitate discourse production of learners so that they can review the types of CF and their judicious use.
- 3) The study enables learners get informed of Corrective Feedback and to improve their productive skills in English language.

Conclusion

Corrective Feedback clarifies the insufficient understanding of the learners of the target language and improves the quality of their spoken and written productions. The present study aimed to find out the corrective feedback received on discourses of learners of English Language in Secondary Schools in Kerala. The study found out that Corrective Feedback is received in moderation by the majority of secondary school students. The study also found that there is a significant difference in the Corrective Feedback received by secondary school students with respect to the type of management of the schools.

References

- [1] Herra, A, & Kulinska, A. (2019). The role of feedback in the process of learning English as a foreign language. *Forum Filologiczne Ateneum*, 127-143. 10.36575/2353- 2912/1(6)2018.127.
- [2] Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The Power of Feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81–112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>
- [3] Rouhi, A., Dibah., M., & Mohebbi, H. (2020). Assessing the effect of giving and receiving written corrective feedback on improving L2 writing accuracy: Does giving and receiving feedback have fair mutual benefit? *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education*, 5
- [4] Thiri, S. (2022). Corrective Feedback in Language Teaching. *Journal of International CulturalStudies*.
- [5] Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., & Hattie, J. (2020). The power of feedback revisited: A metaanalysis of educational feedback research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 3087– 3087. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087>

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IMPROVEMENT OF URBAN EDUCATION IN INDIA THROUGH MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION FOR BETTER AND STRONG NATIONNASIKA

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Abstract

Education is an Important aspect in the Development of nation, by which we can learn how to live in a present fast-growing world. In this Education also Urban education plays a important role in the development of nation. Urban education is a method of schooling that takes place in large, densely populated areas. This covers schooling at Developed and developing Huge populated Metropolitan cities. This paper gives complete study of urban education in the world as well as India over for last several years and presents what are the obstacles which we are facing in the urban education development process and suggests the possible methods to overcome the obstacles for development of nation.

Keywords: *Urban education, Human Development Index, Technical Education Quality Improvement Program*

Introduction

The term education is originated from a Latin word called educare refers to lead or to develop. Education change from man as biological entity into human being. Education is the necessity of life to bridge the gulf between the innate nature of immature child and the social standard. Education unfolds social reality and equips with freedom. Education focuses to improve the lives of the poor and increase the pace of development in a sustainable manner. Education provides people with knowledge and skills that increase their productivity and make them less vulnerable to risks. Education enables rural households to diversify their income-earning opportunities, Education increases resilience, as it prepares individuals to cope with risks for themselves and their family members throughout the life cycle. Now a days Education getting different Diversions at the root level and creating multiple huge opportunities for humans in many sectors like Aerospace, Business, Health, Engineering, Teaching, Manufacturing, Industrial etc. it is giving solutions for non answered questions in the world for over the years. Along with the fruitful outputs in the Education there are several challenges are coming in this process. Policies on the language of instruction can hold the key for making education systems more inclusive for disadvantaged groups.

Urban Education Relation to Human Development Index of the Nation

The Global Literacy Challenge (2008) considers that both ‘developed’ and ‘developing’ regions – the pace of economic and social change is such that learning continues throughout life. Hence, UNESCO visualised ‘education is one of the means of development’. Literacy leads to empowerment, and the right to education includes the right to literacy – an essential requirement for lifelong learning and a vital means of human development. Poverty and illiteracy tend to go hand-in-hand. Education is often less available in poverty-stricken areas. Moreover, even when education is available, a struggling family might need their children to work and earn money instead of going to school. Most of the countries with the lowest literacy are located in South Asia, West Asia, and sub-Saharan Africa—regions which also include most of the poorest countries in the world. Developed countries have better literacy and proportionate infrastructure of education like availability of school in each locality, teacher- student ratio, classrooms etc.

S.No	Name of the country	Total Population	Urban population	Total literacy rate	Urban Literacy Rate	HDI Rank as per 2022 UNDP data
1	Switzerland	8544000	6305000	99%	100%	1
2	Norway	5353000	4403000	100%	100%	2
3	Iceland	338000	317000	99%	100%	3
4	Hong Kong	7429000	7429000	93.30%	93%	4
5	Australia	29522000	25417000	99%	100%	5
6	Denmark	5754000	5057000	99%	100%	6
7	India	1354052000	460780000	77.7%	87.7%	132

Source: united nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Population Dynamics 2018

The above chart representing Comparison between Top Human Development Nations with India. This chart numbers clearly representing a good Literacy country will always gives a peaceful and fast-growing atmosphere for the Country particularly those countries which is having high Urban literacy rate getting top ranks among world in the Human development rankings. basically, Human Development ranking will give a clear idea about a particular nation Development.

Fig (i) Increment of Urban population over the past 60 years throughout the world

The above figure indicating increasing of Urban population in the world over last 60 years and it gives an idea of requirement of infrastructural facilities.

Urban region are characterised by high population density, relatively better civic facilities and people with more impersonal relations. These features not only indicate the nature of urban society, its institutions and people which influences the urban education. High population density in urban area indicates the need of large number of schools, better civic facilities. The quantitative and qualitative aspects of the schools are important for the overall educational development. The empirical studies show that urban village and urban slums are having insufficient infrastructure and manpower. Secondly, teacher-student ratio, active PTA, and effective teaching learning are playing a critical role in qualitative school education. The teaching skills of the teachers is also a main aspect for getting best education. social capital or relationship among people are very impersonal that indicates a weak social bond and having less information beyond self or we can say no information about their surroundings. In today's, urban society and education is very complex in terms of size, heterogeneity, absence of effective measures and most importantly growing unorganised sector. There are multiple providers of education from primary to the zenith levels; their existence widely varies in its structure and sizes, charges from no fee to very high fees. some of the following issues facing in Urban education process are

Socialisation and Culture Assimilation

Education is one form of socialization. Socialisation is a broad term which encompasses formal and informal training through various agencies like family, peer group and community. The socialisation process of rural population those who have migrated to urban areas and are mostly staying in slums and unorganized colonies are very slow. This has resulted in gap between the education level of people residing in slums and normal areas of urban India. In recent times most of the major cities migrant labours and daily wage workers children are getting difficult to get admission in the schools. Even if they are admitted, the children do not get equal treatment from the teacher as that meted out to the other children. Thus cultural assimilation is a big problem in urban areas which has largely kept the children belonging to the migrant community especially labourers in the in-migrating states away in getting admitted and also pursuing education in the urban educational system. Enrolment growth in cities has been blocked and high dropout cases observed which indicates danger of poverty and crime particularly juvenile crime.

Dualism in Education System

Indian education system has 2 types of education provisioning agencies, one in government institutions which is totally/ partially managed and financed by government and the other is private agencies which is managed by a group of people that may include non-profit sector, religious organisations and private initiatives. Private education system is small organised effort focussed on quality education in certain areas, like developed areas and urban centres where people have higher purchasing power.

Gender Gap in Education

The trace of gender discrimination in education is very age old phenomenon observed across the globe and even today we could not bridged it. Education is one basic human right through that we can achieve the goal of gender equality. t literacy of women is an important key to improving health, nutrition and education in the family and to empowering women to participate in decision-making process in society. Investing in formal and non-formal education and training for girls and women, with its exceptionally high

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social and economic return, has proved to be one of the best means of achieving sustainable development and economic growth that is both sustained and sustainable. there are two-thirds of the youth and adults without literacy skills are Urban Education female.

Challenges of Education in Urban Slums

Slums are often observed as places devoid of the basic services, dense, dingy and small houses, unhealthy environment, overcrowding population, inhabited by people having lower socioeconomic status and a breeding ground of crime and deviance. The Census of India defined slum as “residential areas where dwellings are unfit for human habitation” because they are dilapidated, cramped, poorly ventilated, unclean, or “any combination of these factors which are detrimental to the safety and health”. the people living in these locations have lower socio-economic status and are Urban Education most deprived sections of society. Urbanisation is very complex and challenging, complex because diverse urbanisation rate, It is also challenging due to rapid rural-urban migration, lacking regional and urban planning, glaring inequality and expanding slums. The global population increasing but urban population growth is four times faster than that. Based on one survey report out of 65-70% of total population of the world will live in urban areas by 2030, About 2 billion of them will live in slums, primarily in Africa and Asia, lacking access to clean drinking water and working toilets, surrounded by desperation and crime. . In urban India, there was a 45 percent increase in the number of people living in the urban slums from 1981 to 2001. The fast growing urbanisation in developing regions is because of rapid migration and imbalance regional development. It has been observed that the lack of regional and urban planning unable to check migration, as a result, it is increasing both urban poverty and slum dwellers in urban areas.

Measures to Promote Urban Education

Role of Programme and Policies:- The government of India has launched a number for the promotion of literacy and education both in rural and urban areas. some of them are Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Chalta Firta Schools, Khulja Sim Sim Project, YUVA-School Life skills Programme, Vidyalaya Kalyan Samithi. Role JNNURM in Education Infrastructure: Jawaharlal Nehru Urban Renewal Mission is the most popular measures to develop urban cities/ towns of India. Role of international agencies: One of the important measures observed with regard to the invaluable contribution of many international agencies like World Bank, IMF, Asian Development Bank, Islamic Development Bank, USAID, UNESCO, UNICEF etc. in the area of education. Along with the above things certain initiatives taken by Central Government of India to improve teaching standards in India are Subject wise learning, National Achievement Survey, Minimum qualification of teachers, B.Ed. degree structure, Quality education, Equality in education, International exposure, Cultural festivals, Grading system, Integrated data, E- learning material for teachers and students, Innovations in classroom study, Interactive content for students, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Education channels.

Conclusion

Urban education seems very bright when we compare with large rural areas, but the condition is not so good when analyse within urban settings. Within urban areas a large chunk of rural people have migrated to urban areas for better livelihood. Most serious concern is the increasing trends of these marginal groups’ population with growing urbanisation. Their marginalisation is very much reflected in terms of basic amenities such as education, health services, drinking water etc. Here, our thrust is to see their education status and education opportunities available to them. Urban education further creates classes in society due to existence of dual education system, deepens urban poverty and most important of them a breeding ground of deviance or crime.

References

- [1] Jandhyala B. G. Tilak (1983), “Inequality in Education in India”, Indian Journal of Industrial Relations, Vol. 18, No. 3 (January), pp. 375-395
- [2] Thaman, Konai H (2007), “The role of Higher Education in Regional Development in Pacific Island Countries”, (plenary paper of meeting of the Asia Pacific Scientific Committee on research in higher education), 17-19 September 2007.
- [3] <https://tophat.com/glossary/u/urban-education>
- [4] UNESCO (2008), The Global Literacy Challenged, edited by M. Richmond, C. Robinson and M. Sachs-Israel, Division for the Coordination of United Nations Priorities in Education, Paris (France).

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT NEEDS OF TRADITIONAL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Teachers keeping in mind the rising rate of student's enrollment, and the increased demand for traditional teachers, the need for professional development of traditional teachers is keenly felt. The skills needed for teaching in face-to-face environments are not always transferable to traditional transforming settings. There is a pointed change in the way teaching takes place in a traditional format, which calls for an understanding of teacher roles and the competencies prompted by this paradigm shift. A lack of understanding of the pedagogical transformations required by traditional teaching could lead to teacher stress. The purpose of this study was to understand the extent to which educators teaching in traditional settings in Tamilnadu are equipped to work in such traditional teaching and learning environments by relying on specific competencies and skill sets. This understanding would then enable the development of programs designed to traditional teacher's address their professional development needs.

Keywords: *Face-To-Face Environments, Paradigm Shift, Competencies.*

Teachers keeping in her school environment mind the rising rate of student's enrollments and the increased demand for traditional teachers, traditional teaching need for professional development of traditional teachers is keenly felt. Traditional teaching methods focused on the teacher as the only sources of information in the class room. It embraces the ideas of a teacher centered method involving face to face interaction, mainly interacted teacher to students. As an interaction of this disconnect, many teachers who are hired may not have the requisite competencies and skill sets needed to teach in a traditional environment. Teaching and learning environment areas where adequate knowledge will affect Traditional teachers in terms of their competencies and skill sets include the following: discipline, self control, competences, perceptions, involvement and interest instructional strategies and tools; Traditional learning psychology/theories, facilitation skills and issues of technology, and traditional pedagogical content knowledge (Kennedy & Archambault, 2012). Picciano and Seaman (2009) also state that "the keys to the future of traditional options are well- trained instructors, high quality online offerings that align with state standards, effective strategies for maintaining connections with students, [and] cost effective options for districts" (p.15). There are certain misconceptions associated with traditional instruction. One of them is that 'teaching is teaching,' meaning that the skill sets needed in the face-to-face environment are transferable to online teaching without any adjustments. However, this is far from the truth (Davis & Rose, 2007). Traditional pedagogy requires different competencies and skill sets (Bennett & Lockyer, 2004; Jaffee, 2003; and Sieber, 2005). The challenge of teaching traditional without being equipped with appropriate effective teaching strategies and pedagogical foundations is very frustrating to virtual teachers (Brennan, 2003). Another important consideration to follow up on professional development sessions is reinforcement as a way to measure the effectiveness of such traditional training. While designing professional development in suitable for students learning, it is not only important to customize it according to teacher needs, but also to give opportunities for teachers to reinforce what has been taught, as this is crucial to further growth and increased efficacy. Educational research, reforms, policies, and expectations from all sections of society have set high academic standards for students and teachers, especially in terms of 21st- century skill developments. Along with core knowledge instruction, students must also learn the essential skills required for success, such as critical thinking, problem solving, communication, and collaboration in the context of local, national, and global needs. Experts have recommended strong support systems to sustain these educational needs in terms of standards, assessments, curriculum, instructional strategies, and teacher – centered teaching on the student-centered learning environments. The onus of responsibility in terms of achieving these goals cannot solely be placed on teachers as a way to encourage them to become effective agents of change with support and guidance from school leadership. As traditional teaching and learning is still developing as a field of practice and study with skills values increasing, there is a dearth of research in the area of traditional teaching and learning compared to school education, so there is a need for the former sector to develop its own body of research that will identify the best practices in traditional teaching and learning. As school student's settings are unique and learners are different from adult learners in post- secondary environments, professional development should result in the creation of a cadre of "teachers who understand learning as well as teaching, who can address students' needs as well as demand of their disciplines and who can create bridges between students' experiences and curriculum goals". Professional development in an online setting would mean that: Teachers understand what it means to teach traditional, the

associated competencies and skill sets, as well as the rewards and challenges of instruction in traditional learning environments. Teachers have to be proactively involved in their own traditional learning process so that they are equipped with the competencies and skill sets and expected to facilitate student learning by being able to understand learning from the students' perspective. The design and purpose of professional development is to support and empower traditional teachers as well as raise the performance levels of both the educators and their students. This proactive, continuous professional development practice is even more pertinent to the traditional learning environment because of its novel and unique nature, where traditional teaching and problem-solving skills already mastered by the teacher may turn out not to be as effective. There is a need to equip traditional teachers with an understanding of the nature of traditional student-teacher interaction and challenges that arise due to the characteristics of the medium of instruction easily. Moreover, the competencies needed in this field are different from those needed in face-to-face environments; therefore, online teaching requires specialized professional development.

Teacher Qualities

The teacher qualities mentioned by participants were relationship building to motivate students (communication with students and family, positive feedback, understand students' needs, finding the key that motivates students, patience, welcoming, flexibility, ever present in a student's life), understanding the uniqueness of the traditional environment, time- management, understanding diverse cultures and socio-economic status, patience and organizational skills. In their study, identified interaction as the most important learning activity teaching and learning environment. The unique challenges face to face interaction traditional environments are multiplied if there is lack of adequate interaction and consequently communication between learner-instructor interaction, learner-learner interaction, and learner-content interaction, and learner-interface interaction. This deficiency can be dealt with by instructors by creating learning communities, initiating motivational interactions with students to increase student engagement, promoting social presence through interaction, and communication/feedback. All these teacher qualities can be addressed in professional development sessions for traditional instructors where participants understand the foundational aspects of traditional learning and the competencies attached there in. This teaching and learning can only be navigated when instructors in traditional settings are equipped with foundational training focused on the architecture of such traditional learning environments: Teaching and learning connect content, students, and instructional traditional environments, as demonstrated by one respondent: "The traditional learning environment is another important consideration. We've learned that most students do better when there is someone who is immediately available to offer help with concepts. Many high school students are not proactive with their education so they need constant mentoring, support and guidance. The traditional portion of the job seemed to be relatively easy to learn. Learning how to adapt the traditional lesson into a truly supportive in class-lesson face to face is a little tricky". Bring together students, parents, and traditional institutions to track student progress, as highlighted by one other respondent: "The most important recommendation I have for an online teacher preparation is to communicate with students and family in regards to progress and grades". Fill the gap between teacher and student in an face to face learning setting when the latter is disengaged due to lack of face-to-face interactions, as mentioned by one participant: "COMUNICATION at all costs. We do not physically see all of our students; therefore, we need to be in constant contact with our students. Appropriate feedback is essential as well". Understand and connect the diverse student body, as referenced by one participating teacher: "Our school is across the state of tamilnadu. In our classroom, I have students from all areas (Urban, Rural,) and socioeconomic (poverty-riches) and multiple religions (Hindu, Muslim, Christianity, etc). I can see it being important to understand all cultures and traditional environments". Serve as motivational connection between traditional teachers and students, leading to relationship building and consequently increased student engagement. This was expressed by one of the respondents as, "Be patient and positive. Positive interactions and encouragement can lead to little successes and before they know it, the students are zipping through material that they would have believed to be beyond their capabilities".

Professional Development of Traditional Teachers: Reasons

The first reason for providing specialized professional development to traditional teachers has to do with the fact that most of them have the skills development needed for face-to-face instruction, based on which they possess state-issued teaching licenses. However, point out that the skills needed for teaching in face-to-face traditional environments are not always transferable to class room settings. There is a pointed change in the way teaching takes place in a traditional format, which calls for an understanding of teacher roles and the competencies prompted by this paradigm shift. A lack of understanding of the pedagogical transformations required by traditional teaching could lead to teacher stress may be relies to conduct students teacher interaction. The same author also points out that a teacher's "role is at the heart of conflict and ambiguity in organizations and it is suggested that function of the roles and competencies are different from those required in the traditional learning environment". As traditional communication must also be closely

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monitored, instructors have to have control over the finer aspects of communication. To that effect, “although all teachers should possess good communication skills, this is particularly critical in traditional environments where much of the communication occurs without the visual cues associated with face-to-face communications” (Davis & Rose, 2007, p. 9). Teachers are unable to see the moment when students begin to zone out because of learning saturation, as they can physically observe them. Traditional learning students also have fewer opportunities to bond socially when they do not share a physical environment. The period of time before and after class sessions when students in face-to-face environments can interact freely is missing from class room settings, unless instructors are specific about providing such opportunities. These can potentially teaching and learning result in more camaraderie among students, which can reduce cooperation and participation in group work. It can be difficult to encourage the development of trust and camaraderie due to the inherent characteristics of class room settings. Students may be more forthcoming about personal information with each other if they expect their class room test and other activities to be recorded. Therefore, instructors must develop strategies that allow students to interact and share common experiences that build bonds of trust among them.

Conclusion

While designing professional development for traditional teachers, one has to keep in mind the uniqueness of this traditional teaching environment and the resulting challenge of meeting student and teacher needs. The primacy and challenge of addressing the specific needs of online students calls for honing the competencies and skill development sets of the traditional teachers. The implications of this for PD would be to design teaching modules based on teacher qualities and all the other emerging themes detailed above. There is a need for continuous professional development and reinforcement because of the novel and unique nature of traditional teaching in terms of instructional strategies, student-teacher interactions, and the medium of teaching itself. While most online teachers have face-to-face teaching experience and have mastered these learned practices and problem-solving skills, these face-to-face teaching skills may not be compatible with the traditional environment. There is a need to equip teachers with an understanding of the nature of traditional student-teacher interaction and challenges that arise due to the distance caused by the medium of instruction. The professional development sessions may have addressed these issues as well as newer relevant knowledge in terms of emerging skill development techniques.

References

- [1] Bennett, S., & Lockyer, L. (2004). Becoming an online teacher: Adapting to a changed environment for teaching and learning in higher education. *Educational Media International*, 41(3), 231-244.
- [2] Brennan, R. (2003). One size doesn't fit all: Pedagogy in the online environment- volume 1.
- [3] Leabrook, Australia: National Center for the Vocational Educational Research.
- [4] Birman, B., Desimone, L., Garet, M., & Porter, A. (2000). Designing professional development that works. *Educational Leadership*, 57(8), 28-33.
- [5] Davis, N. E., & Rose, R. (2007). Professional development for virtual schooling and online learning. Vienna, VA: iNACOL.
- [6] Kennedy, K., & Archambault, L. (2012). Offering pre-service teachers field experiences in K-12 online learning: A national survey of teacher education programs. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 63(3), 185-200.
- [7] Meloncon, L. (2007). Exploring electronic landscapes: Technological communication online learning, and instructor preparedness. *Technical Communications Quarterly*, 16(1), 31- 55.
- [8] Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- [9] Sieber, J. (2005). Misconceptions and realities about teaching online. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 11(3), 329-340.
- [10] Vaughan, N. D. (2010). A blended community of inquiry approach: Linking student engagement and course redesign. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 13(1-2), 60-65.

AWARENESS OF MINDFULNESS

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Introduction

Mindfulness is the basic human ability to be fully present, aware of where we are and what we're doing, and not overly reactive or overwhelmed by what's going on around us. Further, Mindfulness means maintaining a moment-by-moment awareness of our thoughts, feelings, bodily sensations, and surrounding environment, through a gentle, nurturing lens. According to Jon Kabat-Zinn, in 1979, well-known author and founder of the Stress Reduction Clinic at the University of Massachusetts. "Mindfulness is awareness that arises through paying attention, on purpose, in the present moment, and non-judgmentally." The goal of mindfulness is to cultivate a meta-perspective on one's consciousness and personhood that can foster greater mental and relational harmony. Mindfulness and compassion can help the students build the inner strength and resilience to cultivate and maintain emotional supportiveness for their students in the face of these challenges. Mindfulness involves cultivating a state of present-centered awareness with an attitude of openness and curiosity rather than judgment. Linda Lantieri (2015) introduced the Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL) for implementing mindful teaching in the classroom and to develop integrated personality among the students.

The Main Purpose of Mindfulness

Mindfulness is also a type of meditation practice in which we focus on being intensely aware of what we are sensing, thinking, and experiencing in the present moment, without interpretation, judgment, or attachment. Mindfulness meditation involves a variety of techniques including breathing methods, body scans, and guided imagery; these exercises can help reduce stress, anxiety, tension, and negative emotion from building up.

Mindfulness Training

Mindfulness exercises are ways of paying attention to the present moment using techniques like meditation, breathing, and yoga. Training helps people become more aware of their thoughts, feelings, and body sensations so that instead of being overwhelmed, they're better able to manage them. Mindfulness is a type of meditation in which you focus on being intensely aware of what you're sensing and feeling in the moment, without interpretation or judgment. Attention to what is occurring in the present moment (simply observing thoughts, feelings, sensations as they arise). Attitude that is non-judgmental, curious, and kind

The Difference between Mindfulness and Flow

Flow is a state in which one is completely absorbed in an activity and loses self-awareness. Flow and mindfulness both involve deep concentration—but only flow involves goal-directed behavior. While mindfulness channels concentration entirely toward the present moment, flow channels concentration toward skills and goal achievement, which might include thoughts of the past and future and judgment of those thoughts.

Awareness in the Mind

"Awareness" is when your attention is focused on the situation simply observing with your senses. You are aware through what you see, hear, feel, smell, taste. Thinking separates us from the immediacy of the situation. Awareness gives us direct perception of the situation and allows us to perceive it more accurately.

Mindfulness Help Relieve Anxiety

Mindfulness encompasses awareness and acceptance, which can help people understand and cope with uncomfortable emotions, allowing them to gain control and relief. To cultivate these skills, concentrate on breathing to lengthen and deepen your breaths. Foster an awareness of the five senses. Notice your thoughts and feelings, and practice curiosity and self-compassion. It has been found to decrease depressive symptoms, anxiety, and stress levels, by enhancing practitioners' ability to regulate their emotions and helping them identify and step back from intense negative emotions and feelings. Mindfulness is guided by this idea of observing thoughts and feelings and letting them go, rather than fighting them.

ADHD

People with ADHD may have trouble paying attention, controlling impulsive behaviors (may act without thinking about what the result will be), or be overly active. Although ADHD can't be cured, it can be successfully managed and some symptoms may improve as the child ages. Is mindfulness hard for people with ADHD? "Mindfulness seemed like a great fit for treating ADHD," the idea of sitting for long periods of time watching the mind may be intimidating for those who experience ADHD. "The key is to make the challenge not too big.

Practices for Bringing Mindfulness into Schools

With heightened academic pressure trickling down to kids as early as kindergarten, resulting in less time for play and the arts, Children today are faced with an unprecedented amount of stress and anxiety-25% of 13 to 18 year olds will experience an anxiety disorder according to the National Institutes of Mental Health. Mindfulness "the awareness that emerges through paying attention on purpose, in the present moment, non-judgmentally" - can bring, including reduced levels of stress and anxiety, increased focus and self-regulation, and improved academic performance and sleep, among others.

Mindfulness Training

The MBSR program began in its first iteration in 1979, developed by a scientist who was also a meditator and yogi, on Kabat-Zinn, founder of the Stress Reduction Clinic at the University of Massachusetts Medical School. MBSR, or Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction, is an eight-week mindfulness training program that was created by Jon Kabat-Zinn in 1979 at the University of Massachusetts Medical Center. He initially created it for chronically ill patients who were not responding well to traditional treatments, but it is now used for a wide variety of reasons by hundreds of thousands of people worldwide. Its roots do come from spiritual teachings, as do all mindfulness meditation programs, but it is largely based on proven medical and psychological research. Mindfulness training sessions drew on the well-established method of Mindfulness-which comprised body scan and breathing meditation in the non-yoga group and body scan, breathing meditation, and yoga. In the case of body scan and breathing meditation, a short version (5 to 6 min) and a long version (15 to 17 min) were available.

Five Steps to Mindfulness

- 1) First Mindfulness Exercise: Mindful Breathing.
- 2) Second Mindfulness Exercise: Concentration.
- 3) Third Mindfulness Exercise: Awareness of Your Body.
- 4) Fourth Mindfulness Exercise: Releasing Tension.
- 5) Fifth Exercise: Walking Meditation.

Advancement in technology is also a major reason for increasing distraction for today's students. A major challenge for teachers is to keep them focused on the lesson. A new study suggests that mindfulness education (by Grace Tatter, Posted: January 23, 2019) — lessons on techniques to calm the mind and body — can reduce the negative effects of stress and increase students' ability to stay engaged, helping them stay on track academically and avoid behavior problems.

Conclusion

Most of the Colleges of Education focuses primarily on content and pedagogy, overlooking the very real social, emotional, and cognitive demands of teaching itself. It is the right time to introduce the mindfulness training in the Colleges of Education. Mindfulness can help us to be more effective at reducing conflict and developing more positive ways of relating in the classroom, which can help us feel more job satisfaction. The mindfulness training helps the teachers to bring out the benefits of mindfulness to students, teachers, counsellors, parents, and child-care providers for deepening their own mindfulness practices and to incorporate them into daily life and work. The mindful teachers spend a great amount of time for professional development and learning new techniques that will nurture a learning environment. One technique that helps to establish and maintain a learning environment is practicing and teaching mindfulness.

References

- [1] Wimmer L, Bellingrath S and von Stockhausen L (2020) Mindfulness Training for Improving Attention Regulation in University Students: Is It Effective? and Do Yoga and Homework Matter? *Front. Psychol.* 11:719. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00719
- [2] Bogels S, Hoogstad B, van Dun L, de Schutter S, Restifo K. Mindfulness training for Adolescents with externalizing disorders and their parents. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy.* 2008;36:193–209.

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EFFECT OF IRON YOGA PRACTICES AND MINDFULNESS MEDITATION ON PHYSIOLOGICAL VARIABLE OF SCHOOL LEVEL KHO-KHO PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of iron yoga practices and mindfulness meditation on physiological variable of school level kho-kho players, sixty male students from different school of Salem district acted as subjects for the study. The selected participants were randomly (simple random sample) assigned to one of four groups of fifteen (n=15) each, such as experimental group I, experimental group II, experimental group III and control group. The group I (n=15) underwent mindfulness meditation, group II (n=15) underwent iron yoga, group III (n=15) underwent combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga and group IV (n=15) acted as control. The subjects in control group were not engaged in any activity other their regular curriculum. Vital capacity was selected as dependent variables for this study. The following independent variables were selected for this study such as mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, and combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga. The pre-test and post-test randomized control group design was used as experimental design. The collected data from the four groups prior to and immediately after the training programme on selected criterion variables were statistically analyzed with analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the significant difference between experimental and control groups. Whenever the 'F' ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, the Scheffe's test was applied as post-hoc test to find out paired mean difference. In all the cases 0.05 level of significant was fixed to test the hypothesis. The mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga had significantly improved the participants vital capacity. The combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga had significantly outperformed than mindfulness meditation, iron yoga on the participant's vital capacity.

Keywords: *Mindfulness Meditation, Iron Yoga, Kho-Kho, Vital Capacity*

Introduction

Kho Kho is the game played by 11 players per side in which only 9 players are allowed to play in the field. The game is more popular in the Asian Sub Continent, especially in countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal. Surprisingly Kho Kho is played in South Africa also. Kho Kho playground or pitch is rectangular and it is 29 meters long and 16 meters wide. There are two more rectangles at each end. One side of the rectangle is 16 meters and the other side is 2.75 meters. There are two wooden or iron poles fixed at both the ends of the field. The central lane which touches the poles is 23.5 meters long and 30 cm wide in which the players sit and play. Kho-Kho helps the children to off depression, anxiety, stress, and increase self-esteem. Kho Kho is a outdoor game played by people of all age groups. Playing Kho-Kho keeps children well, strong motivated, enthusiastic and young. It helps in better coordination and flexibility.

Methodology

Sixty male students from different school of Salem district acted as subjects for the study. The selected participants were randomly (simple random sample) assigned to one of four groups of fifteen (n=15) each, such as experimental group I, experimental group II, experimental group III and control group. The group I (n=15) underwent mindfulness meditation, group II (n=15) underwent iron yoga, group III (n=15) underwent combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga and group IV (n=15) acted as control. The subjects in control group were not engaged in any activity other their regular curriculum. Vital capacity was selected as dependent variables for this study. The following independent variables were selected for this study such as mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, and combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga. The pre-test and post-test randomized control group design was used as experimental design. The collected data from the four groups prior to and immediately after the training programme on selected criterion variables were statistically analyzed with analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the significant difference between experimental and control groups. Whenever the 'F' ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant, the Scheffe's test was applied as post-hoc test to find out paired mean difference. In all the cases 0.05 level of significant was fixed to test the hypothesis.

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Training Programme Mindfulness Meditation

As a practice, mindfulness meditation is a nonsectarian form of meditation. It is intended to develop skills of paying attention to ourselves and the world and encourages compassion, acceptance and kindness in meeting whatever is found there. It also brings awareness and presence to a person, helping one to avoid functioning on "autopilot". When mindfulness meditation is practiced formally, the breath is usually used as an anchor for the attention. By following the breath, the mind has something to focus on and gently be brought back to every time it wanders. Attention may also be focused on physical sensations in the body or on the senses of touch, smell, taste, hearing or sight. Daily practice is recommended to develop the mental discipline, stability and concentration that this practice both requires and builds. (Beauchemin,2008)

Iron Yoga

Iron yoga is a unique practice that combines yoga poses with upper body weight training for a full body workout. It lets you reap the benefits of both yoga and weight training with superfast results. While practicing some of your favorite standing and single leg balancing yoga asana, you will incorporate light to moderate dumbbells to work your arms, shoulders, chest, back and core with over 25 different weight training exercises. The result is a full body shaping, toning and sculpting routine. (Graydon Gains L, 2010)

Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

The pre and post test data collected from four groups on vital capacity was statistically examined for significant difference, by applying the analysis of covariance (ANACOVA). Whenever an 'F' ratio for adjusted test was found to be significant for adjusted post-test means, Scheffe's test was followed as a post-hoc test to determine which of the paired mean differences was significant.

Table - I Analysis of Covariance for Pre and Post Tests Data on vital capacity among Experimental Groups of School Level Kho-Kho Players

Test Conditions		CG	MM	IY	MM&IY	S V	SS	Df	MS	'F' Ratio
Pre test	Mean	2.32	2.62	2.58	2.37	B	1.93	3	0.65	1.84
	S.D.	0.6	0.06	0.05	0.05	W	41.13	56	0.35	
Post test	Mean	2.40	2.88	3.03	3.43	B	16.39	3	5.46	12.84*
	S.D.	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.05	W	49.36	56	0.42	
Adjusted post test	Mean	2.55	2.74	2.93	3.53	B	16.24	3	5.41	64.51*
						W	9.65	57	0.08	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence. (The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 3 and 56 and 3 and 57 are 3.16). B-Between, W-Within, SS-Sum of Square, Df-Degrees of Freedom, MS-Means Square

Results of Vital Capacity

The pre test mean and standard deviation on vital capacity of CG, MM, IY, and MM&IY were 2.32 ± 0.06 , 2.62 ± 0.06 , 2.58 ± 0.05 and 2.37 ± 0.05 respectively, the obtained pre test F value of 1.84 was lesser than the required table F value of 3.16. Hence the pre test mean value of mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, and combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga group and control group on vital capacity, before start of the respective treatments were found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 56. Thus this analysis confirmed that the random assignment of subjects into four groups were successful. The post-test means and standard deviation on vital capacity scores of CG, MM, IY, and MM&IY were 2.40 ± 0.07 , 2.88 ± 0.07 , 3.03 ± 0.05 and 3.43 ± 0.05 respectively. The obtained post-test F value of 12.84 was greater than the required table F value of 3.16. Hence the post – test mean value of agility, showed significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 56. Thus the result obtained proved that the interventions namely mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, and combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga on vital capacity produced significantly different improvements between the training groups. The adjusted post-test means on vital capacity scores of CG, MM, IY, and MM&IY were 2.55, 2.74, 2.93 and 3.53 respectively. The obtained adjusted post-test F value 64.51 was greater than the required table F value of 3.16. Hence the post-test mean value of vital capacity, showed significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 56. The end results of analysis of covariance prove that there was significant difference on the selected three trainings and control group on vital capacity. In order to find out which intervention programme used in the present study was the source for the significance of adjusted mean was

tested by Scheffe's post hoc test.

Figure – 1 Comparison of the means on Vital Capacity of the Control Group and three Experimental Group

Table – II The Results of Scheffe’s Post Hoc Test Mean Differences on vital capacity Among Four Groups

CG	MM	IY	MM & IY	Mean Differences	Confidence Interval Value
2.55	2.74			0.19*	0.147
2.55		2.93		0.38*	0.147
2.55			3.53	0.98*	0.147
	2.74	2.93		0.19*	0.147
	2.74		3.53	0.79*	0.147
		2.93	3.53	0.60*	0.147

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

Results of Post - Hoc test on Vital Capacity

The table II show that the pair wise comparisons of between the groups on vital capacity. The paired mean differences of group 1 and 2, group 1 and 3, group 1 and 4 group 2 and 3 group 2 and 4 group 3 and 4 were 0.19, 0.38, 0.98, 0.19, 0.79 and 0.60 greater than the confidential interval value of 0.147. Hence all three comparisons show the significant. The overall observations of the pair wise comparisons indicate that, the selected three training proved better performance on vital capacity compare with control group. Further, between the three trainings the combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga confirms that best in vital capacity, rather than other trainings.

Conclusion

The mindfulness meditation, iron yoga, combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga had significantly improved the participants vital capacity. The combination of mindfulness meditation and iron yoga had significantly outperformed than mindfulness meditation, iron yoga on the participant’s vital capacity.

References

- [1] David k. Miller, Measurement by the Physical Educator, New York.: McGraw-Hill companies, Inc., 2002.
- [2] Debbie Lawrence, Exercise in Water ii ed., London: A&C Black publishers, 2004.
- [3] Chinmayananda, Swami (1962). Meditation and life, the Chinmaya publication Trust, Madras.
- [4] Chakraborty Tamal, Kaushik Samajdar, & Ivlanik Ghosh (2015). Effort of yoga on selected cardiovascular parameter in elderly subject, Indian journal of basic and applied medical research, March vol -4, issue, P · 298-304.
- [5] Barnes, B.L and Nagarkar, S. (1989). Yoga Education and Scholastic Achievement. Indian Journal of Clinical Psychology. 16 (2): 96-98. Barrow & McGee (1979) Practical Approach to Measurement in Physical Education, Henry Kimpton Publishers, London.
- [6] Batrike, Micheal Steven (1978) Influence of Acute Physical Activity and Non cultive Meditation on State Anxiety. Dissertation Abstracts International - 38/ 1 0.
- [7] Davidson, R.J.Kabat-Zinn, J.Schumacher, J.Alternations in brain and immune function produced by mindfulness meditation. Psychoses Med. 2003 65(4)

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR PROMOTING THEMULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

In the current situation multicultural education in an challenging one among the teachers and students in the teaching and learning process. Multicultural education refers to any form of teaching on education which gives individuals an opportunities to examine their social and cultural biases, breaking those biases within them as a result of which their outlook changes which promotes inclusion, democracy, skill acquisition, self reflection, critical thought, etc., through the help of teachers in the school classroom environment.

Keywords: *Multicultural Education, Diversity, Teacher.*

Introduction

According to Baptise, “multicultural education consist of beliefs and explanations that recognizes and values the importance of ethnic and cultural diversity which shapes lifestyles, social experiences, personal identities and educational identities and educational opportunities of individuals, groups and nations. Multicultural education also prescribes what should be done to ensure equitable accessibility and treatment for diverse groups in schools and in the society as a whole.”

What is Multicultural Education

Multicultural education in simple terms is imparting and gaining knowledge of different cultures and developing mutual respect and tolerance towards different cultures. India practices democracy as the form of government. Secularism is preached and practiced in India. It implies that state shall not interfere in any religious matter. Hence the state follows no religion. To promote peace and harmony in the country, it is important to impart multicultural education.

Teaching Strategies

In multicultural classroom blend of students are found from different cultures to form a diverse environment. Some of the teaching strategies which teachers make use are as follows.

Role Playing

It is pretending to play a role of someone in a specific situation. Here individuals get chance to play a role in a social scenario which provide them an opportunity to experience the feeling and sentiments that may not otherwise be exposed to. New issues and subjects can be projected in a classroom by a teacher which will develop new outlook in students.

Exposure to Different Language and Culture

When different cultures starts interacting with each other then students also start to recognise the similarities and differences among their fellow beings and they will be able to realize that even though they are different from one another but still they shares certain common traits which will help to eliminate prejudices and racism and soon they will start accepting and respecting each other which will create a relationship bond between them and will eliminate social distances between them.

Knowledge of Student's Background

For successful multicultural classroom one of the most essential thing is the knowledge about diverse culture. Teacher should take out time and to learn the background about their students. This knowledge should be shared with students while providing learning experiences to them. Through classroom interaction and questioning opportunities will be given to them to share and discuss the learning experiences.

Cooperative Learning

In classroom teacher will develop small heterogeneous groups of students so that they can master various aspect of particular task. By doing so not only the students are motivated to learn but they develop stronger interpersonal relationship. This technique has a positive impact on students because group member become more accepting of classmates who are different.

Project Method

The project method is extremely beneficial for the proper implementation of the multicultural

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curriculum. It is possible to enable students to be multicultural through the project method. There are many types of projects that can be undertaken, for example, gathering information on various social issues, gathering information on different cultural features, gathering information on various environmental issues. In this way students can do innumerable projects of this kind.

Group Discussion

This strategy will stimulate critical thinking within students. It is an excellent strategy for enhancing student motivation, fostering intellectual ability and encouraging democratic habits. This discussion enhances student's textual evidence, balances new ideas with original conclusions. Thus teacher should use discussion on current topic which will develop their insight, logical thinking and in depth situational analysis.

Seminar Method

It is possible to have a comprehensive discussion on various socio-cultural issues through seminar teaching method. Through this teaching method, it is possible to conduct seminar on various cultural diversity and cultural features. This helps in developing a sense of belonging among the students in different cultures. Seminar teaching method is very effective in multicultural education as it focuses on expert opinion on a social issue.

Conclusion

Teachers hold the important role of educating children about the world around them and giving them the tools needed to be successful, contributing members of society out of all social imbalances.

Reference

- [1] Gloria M Ameny-Dixon, International Journal of Scholarly Academic Intellectual Diversity 8 (1), 1-9, 2004
- [2] Lubna Jaffer Mansuri, APH publishing corporation (2011)
- [3] Hassana Alidou, Languages and education in Africa: A comparative and transdisciplinary analysis, 105-131, 2009
- [4] Tuti Budirahayu, Muhammad Saud, International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and ange 30 (3), 36-47, 2020

ANTECEDENTS OF THE CHALLENGES OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN THE EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER ASSISTED COOPERATIVE LEARNING

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Abstract

Computer Assisted Co-Operative Learning (CACL) is a teaching learning pedagogy that has been used widely in schools. CACL created an interactive, pleasant, and safe environment for deep learning. But the application of these strategies showed that there were challenges in the teaching and learning process. The major challenges are the tendency to use traditional approaches to teaching, insufficient understanding of how to establish teamwork, and lack of up-to-date teaching resources. Same way students also faced some challenges that are group hate, group cohesion, loafing, etc. The suggestions to overcome these challenges are adequate time allocation to adjust to the new environment, careful planning, adequate resource allocation, appropriate integration with the existing curriculum, adequate training of teachers and enhancing collaborative work. In research there was, neither limited information on instructors' perception of CACL nor observations on how this strategy is implemented in the secondary education system. This article analyse the past history of the Challengers of Teachers in the effective implementation of computer assisted cooperative learning, and the ways to overcome it.

Keywords: *Antecedents, Cooperative Learning, Computer-Assisted Cooperative Learning And Challenges*

Introduction

The Computer-Assisted Cooperative Learning strategies are based on group success. There is no way one can succeed if the other in the group fails. "Cooperative Learning refers to the methods of instruction that organize the classroom instruction so the groups of 4-6 students work together to reach a common goal. Co-operative learning involves all group members who share in the process, content, and accountability". Computer-assisted cooperative learning strategies are very subjective: answers vary from person to person. It involves students working in groups or mixed-ability groups. After completing their tasks, it required group interdependence and assessments are made individually and the group determined.

Challenges of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning

Much review of research literature indicates the efficacy of computer-assisted cooperative learning. Teachers feel professional pressure to use this teaching strategy and try to implement CACL without adequate training. In classroom applications of these strategies, some binary tensions occurred that is the environment, the group members, and the individual. The size, number, and access to manipulative along with roles that group members took on were the aspects of the environment promoting tensions.

Challenges in Teachers

Curriculum: The syllabus is pre-determined and instructors thought they could teach more content through lectures. Their concern was expressed about the lack of time to complete the syllabus in a stipulated time period. After completing the portion, they spend time asking questions related to that particular topic. They presented the material themselves. Teachers thought that CACL is time-consuming.

Lack of Instructional Strategies: Lack of experience and knowledge about the CACL strategies and how to prepare the learning materials in a proper way is another challenge faced by the instructors. They are not getting any proper guidelines or training to these strategies. So, they failed to apply these in their class very effectively.

Lack of Computer Proficiency: The second problem that language teachers face in CACL is what materials should be suitable for both students and situations. The customized programs designed by the teachers are more effective than the readymade programs. Another problem in this program is, teachers should have a sound knowledge of technology as well. It is not a realistic solution for many language teachers who are not proficient in computer knowledge.

Software-designed Problem: Another problem of applying the CACL strategy in the classroom is what materials are appropriate and suitable for their students and topic. Teachers should have good control over the computer program that can really serve their purpose and benefit the learners. These problems involve

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major several problems firstly it requires teachers to have sufficient knowledge about computer technology and cooperative strategy, second it involves money and time.

Web Material Design Problems: This is a creative approach apart from the adoption of others material on the internet. Teachers need to prepare their own interactive materials on the internet. But the problem is that it can be created by an experienced teacher. It is not a realistic solution for many teachers who are not proficient are not proficiency in computer knowledge.

Confidence: Experienced teachers were found to be less confident in using the technology while their students adapt more easily.

Infrastructure Facility: Proper ways of infrastructure facilities are another challenge of the application of CAEL. Problems with power supply and telephone range issues limited bandwidth and unaffordable higher bandwidth for internet connectivity, high cost of developing infra structures, learner support system, and teaching resources, etc.

Financial Barriers: Financial barriers are mentioned most frequently in the literature by language education practitioners. They include the cost of hardware, software, and maintenance particularly of the most advanced equipment), and extend to some staff development. Froke (1994) said, "Concerning the money, the challenge was unique because of the nature of the technology."

Availability of Computer Hardware and Software: The most significant aspects of computers are hardware and software. The availability of high-quality software is the most pressing challenge in applying new technologies in education (Herschbach, 1994; Miller, 1997)

Technical and Theoretical Knowledge: A lack of technical and theoretical knowledge is another barrier to the use of Computer-assisted Language Learning technology. Not only is there a shortage of knowledge about developing software to promote learning, as shown above, but many instructors do not understand how to use the new technologies. Furthermore, little is known about integrating these new means of learning into an overall plan

Acceptance of Technologies: Assisted Language Learning is a continuing challenge that requires time and commitment. As we approach the 21st century, we realize that technology as such is not the answer to all our problems. What really matters is how we use technology. Computers can/will never substitute teachers but they offer new opportunities for better language practice.

Challenges in Students

Lack of Social Skills: There are many reasons a person may have a social skill deficit. It occurs because of a lack of knowledge, inability to acquire new skill, etc. Students who do not know how to work together. Without instruction and structure will put each other down, boss each other around, and fail to resolve basic task conflicts. It can lead to difficulties with relationships, anxiety, and depression. it can create negative affect physical as well as mental illness.

Group Grade: Team projects which have a group grade create resentments and are unfair. One student does all the work, the rest receive the grade.

Lack of Diversity Skills: Once heterogeneous teams are formed the high achiever looks across the table at the lowest achiever in the class and says, loud enough for everyone to hear, "I don't want that dummy on my team." The lower achiever retaliates with "Nerds suck!"

Avoidance of Failure: A student is afraid to appear dumb in front of his peers and masks the fear of failure by not participating, saying, "This task is stupid," or "Cooperative learning is dumb!"

Between Team Competitions: Only the best teams receive recognition or rewards. After not winning several times, some teams stop trying, finding it face-saving to say "We don't care." They won't admit they really want to win and cannot.

Within Class Tracking: Tournaments are set up so the highest achievers go to the highest tournament table, and the lowest achievers go to the lowest tournament table. After a few times, those at the lowest tournament table realize they are the "dummy table" and drop in self-esteem.

Complex Co-op Lessons: Complex cooperative learning lessons are planned. They take so much time and effort that cooperative learning occurs only occasionally, and the benefits of cooperative learning are not reaped.

Special Materials: Cooperative learning methods are adopted which require special methods and materials. After the curriculum is adapted to the special methods, and materials are laboriously created, the teacher changes grade level or the curriculum focus is shifted; making the materials useless, so cooperative learning is dropped.

No Parent Preparations: The teacher uses the "Guess the Fib" strategy without first explaining it to parents. When Susie comes home from school, her mother asks her what she did in class today. She responds, "Our teacher taught us how to lie!" Her mother is outraged.

Stepping on Sensitive Toes: A teacher uses a Line-Up on the pros and cons of abortion in an attempt to have students take a stance on a social issue and articulate their own point of view. A student goes home

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and reports he had to paraphrase the ideas of a pro-abortion classmate. The anti-abortion parent is outraged, accusing the school of brainwashing his child.

Dependency: Students work almost exclusively in teams. They become dependent on their teammates and do not want to work alone.

No Principal Preparation: A teacher is using the Same/Different strategy in her class. An uninformed principal peeks into the room and walks out saying, "I came to observe you teaching. I see you have the students' playing games. I will come back later when you are teaching."

Lack of Management Strategies: A teacher fails to put a quiet signal in place and becomes exhausted attempting to control the attention of the students.

Off-Task Behaviour: Students are working on a math project in teams. One mentions a bit of hot gossip. The students get completely off task.

No preparation with the Neighbouring Teacher: The students are doing a Team Chat. They become very loud. The teacher next door peeks in and looks aghast, asking, "Have you completely lost control of your classroom?"

No Preparation with the Community: A radio broadcaster who has never seen real cooperative learning in action and who has not reviewed the research, loudly proclaims collaborative learning is the misguided attempt to have students who know very little about a topic teach others who know even less.

Feeling Used; Being Used: A parent of a high achieving student complains his son or daughter is being used, spending time teaching the dummies in the class, rather than learning critical curriculum.

Recommendations for the Effective Implementation of Computer Assisted Cooperative Learning

The main challenge faced in cooperative and collaborative learning is group conflict. Students need to learn to work together. It is not always something that comes naturally. You can teach skills like praising others, taking turns for equal participation, and shared decision making. Teachers who haven't previously used cooperative or collaborative learning might also need to get used to the noise level in the classroom, which is raised during these activities. Group cohesiveness occurs only to the extent that people's needs are satisfied. But how do you foster such cohesiveness? Whenever the dynamics of interpersonal relationships, diverse learning styles, or power imbalances obstruct a group's flow of communication, conflict-resolution strategies can assist students in resolving and diffusing the situation. Students sometimes require assistance and may need to be reassured that they can positively interact with others. But if you remove students, the group learns that conflict should be avoided rather than resolved. Instead, you may want to encourage groups to Listen to Every Member. The idea here is to agree on who does what, and by when. Collaboration takes place around the "how" and "what" questions. Value Each Person's Gifts. Trouble occurs if one student is after marks only and fails to trust others in the group to attain high marks. So rather than welcoming each person's ideas and contributions, the domineering person relies on only one or two to demonstrate their talents. But we know that people are motivated by demonstrating their own individual strengths, not by coasting on another member's abilities. Model Excellence. If one student falls short of the group's expectations, others can help by supporting and encouraging change. However, members should avoid sharp criticism and negative reactions to each other's ideas and insights.

Conclusion

In summary, this paper has explored the challenges of implementing computer-assisted co-operative learning in the classroom faced by students and teachers. The major problem in CACL is associated with hardware and software design and infrastructure facilities and lack of confidence, lack of awareness about-operative teaching strategies, lack of interest, inability of teachers to share responsibility for each group member, lack of technical knowledge etc.

References

- [1] Aronson, E. (1978). *The jigsaw classroom*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- [2] Froke, M. (1994). A vision and promise: Distance education at Penn State, Part1- Toward an experience-based definition. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 42 (2), 16-22.
- [3] Herschbach, D. (1994). *Addressing vocational training and retaining through educational technology: Policy alternatives*. (Information Series No. 276). Columbus, OH: The National Center for Research in Vocational Education.
- [4] Johnson, D.W., & Johnson, R.T. (1975). *Learning together and alone*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [5] Sharan, S., & Sharan Y. (1976). *Small group teaching*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Educational Technology Publications.

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EFFECTIVE LEARNING THROUGH COGNITIVE FLEXIBILITY

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Abstract

The present study aims to investigate Effective Learning through Cognitive Flexibility. The study explains the meaning of learning and cognitive flexibility. Learning is a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning. Cognitive flexibility is the ability to abandon one strategy in favour of a more optimal strategy. Also this study investigates how learning can be effectively done through the cognitive flexibility. It also explains the impact of cognitively flexibility for the students in their learning effect. The study describes the various methods used for effective learning. The study concludes that an inquisitive person can learn more but only a cognitive flexible thinker can do more. Learning concepts alone cannot build a happy environment, changing and adapting where ever and whenever required helps in a sustainable development of human kind and can also make the earth a better planet for living.

Introduction

Learning is “a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning” (Ambrose et al, 2010, p. 3). Learning is the process of promoting/ pick up/ achieve new understanding, behaviours, knowledge, skills, values, attitudes and preferences. It is also the knowledge acquired by systematic study in any field of scholarly application. It is also the modification of the behaviour learnt or practiced through training or experiences. Erudition in any field required copious learning. Cognitive flexibility is the ability to abandon one strategy in favour of a more optimal strategy (Scott, 1962). Not only is cognitive flexibility necessary for breaking old cognitive patterns, but it relates positively to creative performance (Guilford, 1967). In addition, flexible thinking predicts creative performance, the ability to generate new ideas, and the ability to find multiple ways to use one idea (DeDreu et al., 2007; Hirt, Devers, & McCrea, 2008). It was also found that positive mood results in flexible thinking and helps people balance goals, stress levels, and pressure (Dreishbach & Goschke, 2004). Some researchers found that having experiences that were defined as highly unusual and unexpected events (e.g., early parental loss, living abroad, having an immigrant status) were more likely to be creative because the experience was beyond the boundaries of normal daily experiences (Goertzel, Goertzel, & Goertzel, 1978; Leung, Maddux, Galinsky, & Chiu, 2008). Ritter et al. (2012) found that individuals in the Active-Unexpected-Events condition were more cognitively flexible and had significantly more ideas (verbal fluency) than the Active-Normal-Events and Vicarious Unexpected Events conditions.

Cognitive Flexibility in Education

Cognitive flexibility is important for students as they can look at the same problem from different or multiple perspective and adapt quickly to any new situation. The term “Cognitive Flexibility” might be new term but it was always in our culture and evolving around as with the word “Be smart”. It just means that be observant and react or act appropriately. Being vigilant, observant, smart, proactive are the few terms related to cognitive flexibility. Cognitive flexibility is the ability to adapt our behaviour and thinking in response to the environment. When children are asked to think about multiple concepts simultaneously or change their approach to solving a problem, they need to demonstrate flexible thinking for their effective learning.

Impact of Cognitive Flexibility on Learning

Studies shown that individual learning ability depends on cognitive flexibility. According to oxfordlearning.com it is the skill that separates from good learners from so-so learners. Learning becomes fast and easy when cognitive flexibility is strong. Concentration, Perception, Memory and Logical thinking are key factors for a learning. Concentration which is also mentioned as attention is the first step in learning process, it can be paying attention in the classroom or paying attention to details while solving a problem. Perception varies from one to another. This gives more views, ideas and approach to the problem but from all various angles so as to make the work easier and faster. Retention and recalling are also an important part of learning with the help of memory.

Characteristics of Effective Learning

- 1) Playing and exploring

- 2) Active learning
- 3) Creative and Critical thinking

Playing and exploring: Willingness in learning new things, curiosity about objects, people, and events, using sense to explore the world around, initiating activity seeking challenge, showing a 'can do' attitude, taking a risk, engaging in new experiences and learning by trial and error which requires engagement in the activity involved, playing with the data and knowledge what is known and the readiness to 'have a go'. Active Learning: Self Motivated helps in going through hardship while attaining the goal. Maintaining the focus on the activity for a period, fascinated about facts and paying attention to details. Persistence in activity while challenges occur, believing that more effort or different approach will work. Being involved and concentrating, trying, and most importantly enjoying, achieving what is set to do. Creative and Critical thinking: Thinking of ideas, finding ways to solve problem, finding new ways to do things, making links, and noticing the patterns, making predictions, testing ideas, developing ideas of grouping, sequencing to know the causes and effects, planning, making decisions on how to approach the problem and reach the goal, intermittent checking for how the task moving on and changing strategies as needed and reviewing on approach how well did it work. For example, when children are given a problem 1290 divided by 1000, there are more than one method to find solution. Method 1: $1290 \div 1000$ can be solved by regular division method to find the answer as 1.290 and writing the final answer as 1.29 is also one among the correct approach. Method 2: $1290 \div 1000 = 1.290$ because while dividing by 10 exponentials the decimal point moves towards left.

Effective Learning Methods

There are 6 methods that help in effective learning. These methods help the learners

- 1) Retrieval
- 2) Interval
- 3) Varied practice
- 4) Elaboration
- 5) Reflection
- 6) Spaced Repetition

Retrieving data from memory is important in day-to-day activities, like from where the car is parked to learn new skills. Retrieval is the third step in memory process. Repeatedly retrieving concepts from memory is one of the best ways to learn them. Organising any materials / things / data / information always make the work easier while needed again similarly while memorising the concepts it is important to use chunking methods which breaks down large amount of information into smaller units that are easy to understand. Further by making association with already existing knowledge, by using visual cues like graphs, charts and mind map helps to recollect quicker. Creating mnemonics such as acronyms and rhyme to remember a particular year while learning history and remembering a big data in form of a story also helps. By writing it down says researchers, meaning when notes take in a hand written format rather than typing are effective. When taking notes by hand probably we need to be more selective with words so that only key points are noted by focusing more. Spaced repetition is an effective way in learning effectively as it improves brain's ability in recalling the stored data. All these techniques are tools of effective learning and cognitive flexibility is an approach to these techniques so as to make the learning more effective. Every child is unique. Everyone has their own learning patterns and techniques.

Conclusion

An inquisitive person can learn more but only a cognitive flexible thinker can do more. Learning concepts alone cannot build a happy environment, changing and adapting where ever and whenever required helps in a sustainable development of human kind and can also make the earth a better planet for living.

References

- [1] Dr. Albrecht (Sep 2012), Brain Building. Ambrose et al, (2010), How learning works.
- [2] DeDreu et al., 2007; Hirt, Devers, & McCrea (2008), Behavioural Activation Links to Creativity Because of Increased Cognitive Flexibility.
- [3] Dreishbach & Goschke (2004), Brain and Cognition, Volume 60, Issue 1 Guilford (1967), Creativity: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow.
- [4] Leung, Maddux, Galinsky, & Chiu (2008), Multicultural Experience Enhances Creativity: The When and How.
- [5] Ritter et al. (2012), Diversifying Experiences Enhance Cognitive Flexibility – Journal of Social Psychology 48 (2012) 961-964
- [6] Scott (1962), Cognitive complexity and Cognitive flexibility.

CHANGING WORLD : INTERGENERATIONAL LEARNING AND INTERCULTURAL EDUCATION WITH RESPECT TO SENIOR CITIZENS

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Abstract

Intergenerational learning and intercultural education are important for creating a more inclusive and equitable society which help to break down stereotypes, promote mutual understanding and respect and encourage active participation in a diverse and changing world. For many senior citizens, this process is prolonged out and challenging, accompanied by memories, inactivity, and inability to make new connections. One of the crucial things in this regard is the necessity to keep senior citizens engaged through education. Younger generation can learn from the experiences and knowledge of senior citizens, while senior citizens can share their skills, wisdom, and perspectives with the younger generation. Together, intergenerational learning and intercultural education can be a powerful tool for fostering creativity and innovation. By bringing together individuals from different generations and cultures, we can create a rich perspectives of knowledge, experiences, and ideas that can inspire new ways of thinking and problem-solving. This article reviews the principles and collaboration of intergenerational learning and intercultural education and the challenges, educational measures which fosters mutual understanding and respect, promoting empathy and tolerance, building intergenerational and intercultural skills, and creating opportunities for personal growth and development.

Keywords : *Intergenerational Learning; Intercultural Education, Senior Citizens*

Introduction

The natural process of harnessing human lifelong experience as later life learning typically relates to an ultimate 'fourth age' life cycle completion stage as well as an earlier 'third age' stage (Richards, 2019). Intergenerational learning is the sharing of knowledge, skills, and experience between generations, frequently with the intention of fostering respect and understanding between them. On the other extreme, intercultural education is the process of teaching and learning about many cultures and their traditions, viewpoints, and values with the aim of fostering cultural understanding and respect. The development of a more equitable and inclusive society is thought to benefit from both intergenerational learning and intercultural education. Intergenerational learning can take many different forms, including mentoring programmes, workshops for all ages, and volunteer work. It can occur in both formal contexts like classrooms and institutions as well as informal ones like families and communities. Increased understanding and appreciation of various viewpoints, greater intergenerational communication and social connections and the transfer of important skills and knowledge are all positives of intergenerational learning. By empowering students with the understanding and abilities to communicate effectively with senior citizens from different cultural backgrounds, intercultural education aims to advance cultural understanding and respect. This can involve gaining knowledge of many cultures, histories, and languages as well as enhancing one's ability to think critically and solve problems in order to deal with cultural differences. Both official parameters schools and universities and informal parameters like communities and youth organizations can be used for intercultural education. For the purpose of fostering a society that is more inclusive and equitable, intergenerational learning and intercultural education are both crucial. They can aid in avoiding misconceptions, fostering respect and understanding between senior citizens and younger generations to stimulate involvement in a diverse and changing world.

Some Definitions from Authors

"Intergenerational learning is not only about the transfer of knowledge, but also about the transmission of values, beliefs, and culture." - David Istance, former Director of the UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning. According to UNESCO, intercultural education should respect "the cultural identity of the learner through the provision of culturally appropriate and responsive quality education for all", provide "every learner with the cultural knowledge, attitudes and skills necessary to achieve active and full participation in society" and, finally, provide "all learners with cultural knowledge, attitudes and skills that enable them to contribute to respect, understanding and solidarity among individuals, ethnic, social, cultural and religious groups and nations" Ya Ying Huang, the investigator of Higher Education SPROUT Project USR-HUB sub- project 1, claimed, "Learning how to communicate with fellows from different cultures and generations is now a must-needed. Nation Taiwan Ocean University (NTOU), as the base of intercultural co-

learning, promotes intercultural understanding between international students and old people."

The Principles

Intergenerational learning is guided by principles such as mutual respect, active participation, shared responsibility, inclusive, flexibility, intergenerational interactions, cultural transmission, and long-term sustainability. These principles help ensure that the learning process is inclusive, collaborative, and beneficial for all involved. Intercultural education is guided by principles such as recognizing and valuing cultural diversity, promoting mutual understanding and respect, encouraging critical thinking and active participation, fostering a sense of belonging and inclusive, providing opportunities for intercultural exchange and dialogue, incorporating diverse perspectives and experiences into the curriculum, and empowering individuals to navigate and negotiate different cultures. Senior citizens everywhere are increasingly vulnerable, isolated and prone to rising depression rates, all augmented by the reinforcement of a modern life narrative that learning as well as life purpose ends at either retirement or a certain age (Richards, 2019). UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning(2021) has published about the Hehai Senior School, an adult education school, became a partner, conducting various intergenerational learning activities between older adult learners and younger students. The activities were implemented by a project team consisting of school managers and class teachers (from Longhutong and Hehai schools) as well as education experts. In order to develop generational intelligence, it is necessary to educate specific knowledge, skills, and attitudes, including maintaining openness to other generations and other cultures, withholding judgment, respecting and valuing differences and tolerating ambiguity Carmen Requena(2018). The intercultural team at the Center for Intercultural and International Education (CIIE), (2016) believes that by equipping students, leaders and educators with the intercultural skills they need creates opportunities for justice, mutuality, respect, equality, equity and peacemaking.

In the year 2016, Tereshkina Tatiana and Tereshchenko Svetlana conducted a research on "Concept of intergenerational and intercultural approaches in the education for the third age people in Saint Petersburg (Russia)" has stated in recent years, there has been a decrease in the discrimination of people working with older people, an increase in their educational and retraining opportunities, and new incentives for both formal and non-formal education. Third- age education was currently emerging in St. Petersburg. Corrigan,T., McNamara, G. and O'Hara, J. (2013) has conducted a research on "Intergenerational Learning: A Valuable Learning Experience for Higher Education Students"concluded that an excellent methodology for supporting transformative education is intergenerational learning. People with generational intelligence are able to observe, evaluate, analyse, interpret, and, finally, relate to others in variable generational and cultural keys Dearnorff (2006).Overall, research in this field reveals that intergenerational and intercultural learning can be mutually beneficial and have a good impact on people and communities. Collaboration between intergenerational learning and intercultural education can lead to a number of benefits:

- 1) **Greater cultural knowledge:** Can get a more thorough understanding of cultural traditions and viewpoints by learning from both older and younger generations as well as people from other cultures.
- 2) **Increased Communication skills:** Communication skills are improved when different generations and cultures work together.It can help senior citizen and younger generations to acquire the abilities necessary to speak clearly from various backgrounds.
- 3) **Increased empathy and respect:** Collaboration and reciprocal learning can help senior citizen and younger generations learn to accept and value the opinions and experiences of others, which fosters better empathy and understanding.
- 4) **Preservation of cultural heritage:** Collaboration across generations and cultures can aid in the preservation of cultural traditions and history, which otherwise fear being lost if it is not passed down from one generation to the next.
- 5) **Greater ability to solve problems:** Working together across generations and cultures can result in the development of innovative solutions and fresh viewpoints on tackling problems.
- 6) A sense of community and belonging:Collaboration between generations and cultures can provide senior citizens and younger generations with a feeling of community and belonging by connecting them to their common history and heritage.

Some Challenges for Both Intergenerational Learning and Intercultural Education May Include:

- 1) Bridging the gap between different perspectives and experiences.
- 2) Addressing stereotypes and biases that may exist between different groups.
- 3) Finding common ground and shared understanding among individuals from diverse backgrounds.
- 4) Ensuring that the curriculum and teaching methods are inclusive and culturally responsive.
- 5) Creating safe and respectful learning environments that allow for open dialogue and the sharing of diverse perspectives.
- 6) Overcoming language barriers, especially in the case of intercultural education.

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7)Addressing the power imbalances that may exist between different groups and working to create equity in the classroom.

8)Navigating sensitive or controversial topics that may arise in discussions or activities.

Figueredo-Canosa et al., (2020), reviews in the World Declaration on Higher Education of UNESCO “It was indicated that higher education requires a renewal of the contents, methods, practices and means of transmission of knowledge, which must be based on new types of links and collaboration with the community, and a deep structural transformation”. Educational Measures that can be taken to address the challenges in intergenerational learning and intercultural education include Partnering with local senior centers or community organizations to create opportunities for intergenerational learning and interaction, such as mentorship programs or intergenerational classes Providing training for senior citizens on technology and digital literacy to help bridge the gap between generations in terms of technology use Creating opportunities for students to learn about and from the life experiences of senior citizens through oral history projects or intergenerational storytelling Incorporating the perspectives and contributions of senior citizens in the curriculum, through the study of historical events or personal narrative. Using culturally responsive teaching methods that take into account the cultural backgrounds and experiences of students. Providing opportunities for students to learn about and reflect on their own cultural identities, as well as those of their classmates. Incorporating service-learning or community engagement projects that allow students to interact with and learn from senior citizens from different cultures in real-world contexts

Conclusion

Intergenerational learning and intercultural education both have the potential to be highly educational and creative experiences for individuals of all ages. They can foster mutual understanding and respect, broaden perspectives, and inspire creativity and innovation. Intergenerational learning is a cultural transmission process, through which knowledge, skills, values, and culture are passed on from one generation to the next. Intercultural education can provide individuals with the skills needed to navigate and thrive in a diverse and multicultural world. By learning about different cultures and ways of life, individuals can develop a more empathetic and tolerant perspective. Intergenerational learning programs can also provide senior citizens with the opportunity to share their own knowledge and skills with younger generations, which can help to promote feelings of self-worth and self-esteem. Intergenerational learning and intercultural education are important forms of education that can provide student with valuable perspectives, experiences, and skills. Incorporating these forms of education into school curriculum with respect to senior citizens can help students become more open minded, culturally aware and better prepared with globalized world. There are many ways that intergenerational learning and intercultural education can be integrated into the curriculum, including through guest speakers, mentors, community projects, cultural courses, international exchanges and inclusive teaching methods. Overall, intergenerational learning and intercultural education for senior citizens can be valuable and enriching experience that can help senior citizens to stay engages and active, expand their social networks and cultural understanding and improve their cognitive function.

References

- [1] Carmen Requena, M. D., Swift, H. J., Naegele, L., Zwamborn, M., Metz, S., H. Bosems, W. P., & Hoof, J. V. (2018, May 23). Educational Methods Using Intergenerational Interaction to Fight Ageism. Educational Methods Using Intergenerational Interaction to Fight Ageism | SpringerLink. Retrieved January 19, 2023, from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-73820-8_23
- [2] Corrigan, T., McNamara, G. & O'Hara, J. (2013). Intergenerational learning: A valuable learning experience for higher education students, *Eğitim Araştırmaları, Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 52, 117-136. Retrieved January 16, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1060383.pdf>
- [3] Deardorff, D. K. (2006). Identification and Assessment of Intercultural Competence as a Student Outcome of Internationalization. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(3), 241–266. Retrieved January 19, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306287002>
- [4] Figueredo-Canosa, V., Jiménez, L. O., Romero, C. S., & López Berlanga, M. C. (2020, March 20). Teacher Training in Intercultural Education: Teacher Perceptions. MDPI. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/10/3/81>
- [5] First Intercultural and Intergenerational Co-Learning: International students & Taiwanese older people. (n.d.). First Intercultural and Intergenerational Co-Learning: International Students & Taiwanese Older People. Retrieved January 22, 2023, from <https://mprp.ntou.edu.tw/p/406-1017-80785,r1479.php?Lang=en>
- [6] Intercultural Education. (2016, April 27). CIIE. Retrieved January 21, 2023, from
- [7] <https://www.goshen.edu/ciie/intercultural/>

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DROPOUT AS A CHALLENGE TO THE GROWING DEMAND OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

India is a developing nation. Since its independence, Government of India has been working hand in hand with various non-government and private organizations for the upliftment of its masses along with education. Whereas primary education has been mandated by the Government of India in its constitution, Higher Education suffers. Since India inhabits the largest number of poor people in the world, attainment of higher education is a dream to many. Irrespective of the various efforts by the government to make Higher Education available to all, the students who graduate is very low as compared to the number of students passing Senior Secondary level. This paper attempts to underline the problem of dropout by students at Higher Education level and factors responsible for it.

Introduction

India is a diverse country. With the second largest population in the world, it is among one of the fastest developing countries with its diversified culture, geographical locations, different religions and different standards of living. The country has a rich history dating back to thousands of years with the record of earliest civilizations having inhabited. As such, the growth and regrowth of Indian society as a thriving society has its own charm and own individuality. Indian society, as compared to the societies across the world is a bit more complex in its structure and function. Thus, posing a good deal of challenge to the ruling governments in order to cater to the needs of its diversified components. One of the major challenges being Education.

Need, Importance and Problems of Higher Education

In modern times, education is often associated with vocation. Large number of students opt for education in the hopes of attaining a degree that will help them secure a job and make a career. Hence, education at its higher level is often associated with the job attainment. The higher the level of education, the better the availability of job opportunities and vice-versa. But the increasing demand of Higher education in India is leading to the increased stress and responsibilities on the government for the availability of educational opportunities to all. Every year, lakhs of students pass their senior secondary examinations, but accommodating lakhs of students in institutes of Higher education is the biggest challenge to the authorities. Government and many non-government organizations are working hand in hand for the provision of Higher education to the maximum number of students they can cater to. It's the privilege of many to get enrolled in colleges as the completion is very tough. In many cases, higher education is attained by the students belonging to the higher strata of the society, wherein students have to pay for their education. Irrespective of the fact that government funded colleges are cheap, but the competition in securing an admission in those colleges is very high, hence only highly meritorious students get through. Private colleges on the other hand are available to all, but, they are on the costlier side of the financial scale and not affordable to all. Hence, monitoring and retention of students in higher education is often neglected. Since authorities are busy with making higher education available to all, the question of retention is rarely thought of and explored. Wherein many students complete the course they are enrolled in, many others leave the course halfway and drop out. Drop out can be seen at all levels of education. It is one of the biggest threats to the attainment of 100% literacy of any country. Many studies have been conducted in order to list out the factors contributing towards dropout.

Review of Related Literature

Throughout ages, the education and factors affecting education has been studied by various academicians, educationists and researchers, thereby building a complex model of factors affecting education at different levels. Many researches from India and abroad have tried to list out the factors affecting education in order to list out the remedial measures for tackling the problem so that maximum number of students can be retained in Educational institutions and education be made available for all. Time and again, studies have constantly reported that the socio-economic status (usually measured by the education of the parents and their earnings), is a great indicator of the educational achievement and dropout behaviour (Ekstrom et al., 1986; Bryk and Thum, 1989; Rumberger, 1995; Rumberger & Larson, 1998; McNeal, 1999; Pong & Ju, 2000). At Midwestern Research University, Li and Killian, studied the patterns of attrition in 1999 through

telephonic interviews and reported that the major reason for the leaving the university by the students was the student/institutional mismatch. Further, they reported that there are a variety of reasons (for leaving the university) given by the students including personal and family problems, financial difficulties, academic factors, etc. Different facets of teaching-learning as well have been found to be associated with dropping out. Poor teaching-learning process leads to low motivation and low comprehension among the learners, and ultimately dropping out by the students (Davis & Dupper 2004; Chaudhary et al, 2005). Hence, when the teachers do not plan their work in advance, do not prepare their lesson plans and work schedule, do not check the notebooks and homework of the students, or remain absent from the classes, no learning takes place (Ghuman & Lloyd 2007). Such an environment has a negative influence on the attendance of the students in the classroom which ultimately leads to the difficulty in the retention of the students in the institute. Studies have also implied that poor scholastic accomplishments prompt dropping out (Ekstrom et al., 1986; Goldschmidt & Wang, 1999; Rumberger, 1995; Rumberger & Larson, 1998; Swanson & Scheider, 1999; Colclough et al 2000; Boyle et al, 2002; Hunter and May, 2003; Liu 2004). Studies also support the notion that dropout is affected by both, the social as well as the academic achievements of the understudies. An evaluation of the above studies signifies that the ultimate decision of the student to drop out originates from a number of sources.

Factors Responsible for Dropout

Various studies have listed the major causes of dropout in different cultures and societies across the globe, some of the widely reported factors are listed below;

Poverty: As it has been widely spoken about, poverty is a root cause of all evils and the field of education is no exception. India has been fighting towards the upliftment of its citizens since its independence. Even after 75 years of its independence, a vast portion of its population is poor. According to Global Multidimensional Poverty Index 2022, India has uplifted 41.5 crore of its people off poverty. India holds the record of having the largest number of poor people in the world (228.9 million) in 2020. In a country where poverty is the most common issue to a large portion of its population, opting for higher education is a colossal task in itself. Wherein people find it difficult to eat, paying college fee and spending time in college rather than earning is almost impossible.

Lack of Jobs: Due to the rapid growth in industrialization and information technology, the increase in the number of white collar as well as blue collar jobs has been recorded worldwide. But, irrespective of the availability of jobs in the market, a vast population of the country is jobless/unemployed. The recent global pandemic has added to it. The number of the jobs available is not sufficient enough to cater to the large portion of population. As such, many educated people have to opt for blue collar jobs thus hitting the "concept of higher education for securing jobs" prevalent cross the country. This section of population motivates others for leaving education early to secure some small vocation as no jobs will be available for them once they come out of college, thereby adding to the number of students dropping out each year.

Death of a parent: In many cases, it has been reported that students leave education following the death of one or both of their parents. When the familial support and emotional support provided by parents is compromised, education gets affected.

Separation of parents: As per some studies, the separation of parents was also reported as the cause of dropout by the children.

Family responsibility: Many times, students leave studies in order to secure some vocation to help their family financially. More often than not, taking care of poor parents and looking after the education and marriage of the siblings leads to the dropping out by the students. Increase in the family responsibility of a student pushes the students to drop out of their course and focus on the fulfillment of those responsibilities.

Drugs and alcohol: Alcohol and drugs also add to the problem of dropping out by the students at college level. Whereas government and non-government organizations are working hand in hand to solve the problem of drug abuse in many places across the country, it still remains one of the major areas where efforts and positive intervention by the locals as well as authorities are required

Thefts and crimes: Thefts and other crimes constitute a small portion to a number of factors why students drop out. Even though number is small, but it has a significant impact on the decision of the students to drop out.

Early marriages: Early marriages have been reported to be one of the leading causes of dropout among the female students across some cultures of the world including India. In some societies, women are expected to get married and "settle down" as early as possible. Even if the parents or other family members would like their girl child to study, societal pressure is enough for them to change their decision and get them married. In these societies, the notion of educating their girl child is perceived as a menace, since it gets difficult to find a prospective match for educated girls in future. Hence, even those who are willing to get their girls educated, take them out of college and get them married instead.

Support in household work: In some households, girls are burdened with the responsibility of the

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other members of the family by cooking, cleaning etc. These girls find it difficult to focus on studies in addition to the household work thus leading to dropout. In many cultures across the world, boys are refrained from doing household work, in those homes, girls are burdened with extra work like household chores, cleaning, cooking, etc., hence creating hinderances in their educational attainment and they drop out.

Peer pressure: Peer pressure can impact the thinking of a child in many ways. Psychologists, from time to time have pointed out the impact of peer pressure on the overall development of a child especially emotional development. It is a well-known proverb that *a man is known by the company he keeps*. Same is in case of education. If a child associates him/herself with those people who are against the idea of education, s/he automatically develops the same views regarding the same. Apart from that, in order to identify him/herself to be a part of a group, a person constantly tries to follow the same ideology as propagated by that group.

Order of birth: According to some studies, the order of birth affects the decision of a student to drop out. Many times, it has been seen that elder children are often considered to be the ones to be more responsible towards their younger siblings. Taking care of younger siblings in absence of their parents is the most common happening. While parents go to work, elder children take care of their younger siblings thereby feeding them, cleaning them, taking care of them. In this case, the education of the elder child is often compromised.

Low interest in studies: Lack of interest in studies often leads to dropout by the students. When students do not find their classes interesting, they get involved with other things, and when this becomes a norm for them, education loses its importance to them and they drop out without regret.

Failure: Failing to pass an examination also leads to drop out. When students fail the same exam once or twice, they lose interest and will to qualify and perceive education as an unnecessary burden on them that they are unable to carry. Low self-respect among the students failing in exams causes them to face adjustment issues among their peers hence pushing them to drop out.

Lack of motivation: Sometimes, even if everything is in place, lack of motivation causes a student to drop out. When a person is not motivated enough to achieve its goal, the goal is never achieved.

Curriculum and coursework: Many studies have reported that students drop out because they cannot connect their curriculum and coursework with their day to day life. As such, these students feel education as an extra burden on them in addition to their day to day problems. In many scenarios, a student needs to work after classes and doesn't get time for homework and assignments, in these cases, homework and assignments burden a student causing him/her to drop out.

Geographical location of institute: The geographical location of an educational institute also impacts the decision of the student to drop out. Many researchers have reported that a child dropped out because travelling to the educational institute daily was a problem. In far flung areas, the number of educational institutions catering to the population is low and colleges and other institutions of higher learning are far from area. In these cases, even if a student wants to study, either s/he has to stay away from home (near to the college) to study, or travel long distances daily in order to reach the college. Sometimes both become difficult and a student drops out.

Inappropriate methods of teaching: Many students have cited the faulty methods of teaching as a reason for their drop out. Even though the number is small, but faulty methods of teaching have been reported as a reason for dropout by the students by many researchers

Inadequate facilities and resources: Higher education requires advanced facilities and infrastructure as compared to primary or secondary education. In many places the facilities and resources catering to higher education are not enough, students lose motivation to learn and hence drop out.

Lack of availability of colleges catering to minority: In some cultures, it becomes difficult to educate the female students as the society they are living in are patriarchal in nature. Even though students want to learn, parents are hesitant to send their girl students to places where other genders also study. Many times, people don't send their children to the institutes where students from other backgrounds study. It has been reported in many studies related to tribal population. In such scenarios, making colleges exclusive to those sections is very difficult. Even though the number of colleges catering to minority groups and females are increasing in number, a vast number of students from the population remains dropouts or uneducated.

Suggestions

Financial support in the form of scholarships and fellowships for the students from low income families. Irrespective of the fact that many scholarships are available to the students for low income families, but they are not enough to the present population of the needy and most of them are available till secondary level of education. Higher education lacks appropriate number of scholarships and fellowships. Proper counselling to the parents of students should be provided in order to highlight the importance of higher education for their children and availability of job markets to them. Irrespective of the fact that government has come up with number of financial schemes and programs in order to tackle the issue of education of minorities, private sector should contribute towards the growth of these sectors too. NGOs and recruiting firms

should walk hand in hand for the proper provision of jobs to the existing degree holders and create jobs for them whenever possible. In addition to the existing curriculum, importance of extra-curricular activities should be emphasized in colleges. Development of practical skills should also be focused upon in addition to the traditional knowledge imparting phenomenon. This will help students to create their own vocation in case they fail to secure a job in firms and industries. Creation and monitoring of student placement cells in the institutions of higher learning should be there that will ensure the placement of students in the job market after the completion of education, this will help other students to opt for higher education and employ existing graduates. Guidance and counselling cells should be created and monitored in every college so that students can be effectively guided whenever faced with problems and remedial measures be provided to them. Existing curriculum should be integrated with day to day life of the students so that they will find application of their studies in day to day activities thereby helping in their retention in a course. Organization of job fairs and other vocational platforms in colleges regularly so that students will be motivated to stay in a course.

References

- [1] Chugh, S. (2011). Dropout in Secondary Education; A Study of Children Living in Slums of Delhi. NUEPA Occasional Paper 37. National University of Educational Planning and Administration New Delhi.
- [2] Grau-Valladosera, J., & Minguillón, J. (2014). Rethinking dropout in online higher education: The case of University Oberta de Catalunya. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 15(1). doi:10.19173/irrodl.v15i1.1628
- [3] Lee, Y., & Choi, J. (2011). A review of online course dropout research: Implications for practice and future research. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 59(5), 593–618. doi:10.1007/s11423-010-9177-y
- [4] Li, G., and Killian, T. Students who left college: An examination of their characteristics and reasons for leaving. *AIR Forum Papers*, (ERIC ED 433 779), 1999
- [5] Tinto, V. (1975). Dropout from higher education: A theoretical synthesis of recent research. *Review of educational research*, 45(1), 89-125.
- [6] doi:10.3102/00346543045001089
- [7] Tinto, V. (1982). Defining dropout: A matter of perspective. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 1982(36), 3–15. doi:10.1002/ir.37019823603
- [8] Tinto, V. (2015). Through the eyes of students. *Journal of College Student Retention*, 19(3), 254–269. doi:10.1177/1521025115621917
- [9] Xavier, M., & Meneses, J. (2020). Dropout in online higher education: A scoping review from 2014 to 2018. Barcelona: eLearn Center, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10609/114826>

DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIMEDIA PACKAGE IN TEACHING PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPT IN AT B.ED TRAINEES

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Abstract

Multimedia technologies tools are playing very important role in effective teaching learning process. The purpose of paper is to find out the impact of multimedia package to enhance psychological concept B.Ed trainees are often faced the difficulties to understand the developmental theories. Now a day, students have interested to know everything in psychology but they are showing wide range of difficulties to learn the developmental theories student teacher trainees are often faced the difficulties to learn the concept of developmental theories. As teacher to make efforts to teach psychological concept very easy with the help of multimedia package. The study was conducted on B.Ed. students consists of the students from in private B.Ed. college only in sivaganga. Findings of the study revealed that the multimedia package is very effective to learn psychological concept than traditional method of teaching. Multimedia tends to mean erudition in both manufacture and presentation strategies are electronic media strategies.

Keywords: *Multimedia Package, Media Integration, Autonomy Learning, Psychological.*

Introduction

Teaching has traditionally been associated with classroom instructions on a blackboard with the instructor dependent almost entirely on oratory and presentation skills for holding the attention of the class. From a student's perspective had to keep pace with the instructor's pace, which meant that the slower student was at a natural disadvantage. Similarly some students were more interested in a more in-depth study than the others. Since, access to information was neither easy nor inexpensive, and these variables had always posed a major barrier to learning. Ever since the advent of information technology, the scenario has changed dramatically. Today, the instructor has a repertoire of information technologies. To make the lecture not only more interesting but also more informative, there are advanced electronic teaching tools available. [FloralJeya & Saravanakumar[2022] These vary from simple slide presentations to full-blown multimedia presentations which have video clippings, sound effects, animation and graphics to explain even the most abstruse subjects in a simple and easy to understand manner.

Multimedia Packages

Media are used to the learner achieve the learning objectives more effectively and efficiently. The common instructional media are chalk-board, charts, module, video, T.V, film, radio etc. Some of these media are used to create readiness in the learners for learners' experiences. Some media helps to learn individually or in small groups. So, integration of different media helps the teacher make teaching learning process easy. The teacher can combine also one or more media. Multimedia packages are the instructional kits including all resources needed to provide learning in a specific area. The instructional materials are provided after careful planning. So that provides learning experiences for bringing out the desired learning outcomes and realise the pre-specified objectives. These resources materials are validated and evaluated for their effectiveness in their specific use in the classrooms. The teacher has to use different resources in intergraded manner.

Media Integration

Integration generally means combing parts so that work together or form a whole. In information technology integrated media is a new form of media content creation that cohesively integrates content and context across multiple platforms. Such as web, film, print, live event etc...Media integration includes tractional context storytelling and advertising [Floral Jeya.S, & Saravanakumar.AR [2022],It provides real learning experience among the students and also enhances understanding and retention ability.

Methodology of the Study

Experimental methods the parallel group design was adopted in the study. Control group was taught by traditional method and experimental group was instructed by multimedia package. Sample:The investigators have selected 60 B.Ed. students from private are B.Ed. College only in Sivagangai. Sample random technique was used in the study. Tools used for the study:Multimedia package prepared by the investigator and achievement test. Statistical Techniques Used; Mean, Standard deviation, 't'- test, Pearson's moment correlation were used for statistical analysis of the data.

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Objectives

- 1) To find out the pre-test mean scores of two groups of students in psychological concept.
- 2) To find out the post-test mean scores of two groups of students in psychological concept.
- 3) To find out the mean gain scores of experimental group students in psychological concept
- 4) To find out the mean gain scores of control group of students in psychological concept

Hypotheses

- 1) There is no difference between the mean scores of pre-test between two groups of students in psychological concept.
- 2) There is no difference between the mean scores of post-test between two groups of students in psychological concept.
- 3) There is no difference between the mean scores of experimental group students in psychological concept.
- 4) There is no difference between the mean scores of control group students in psychological concept.

Data Analysis and Discussions

Hypothesis1: There is no difference between the mean scores of pre-test between two groups of students in psychological concepts. The hypotheses were tested at $P < 0.05$ level of students.

Table:1

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Calculated-t-Value
Group-1	30	22.30	2.19	0.49
Group-2	30	19.89	1.98	0.19

Table-1 Indicates that the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level. The students of the group- 1 do not differ significantly from the students of the group-2 in the mean achievement test scores at the pre-test level.

Hypothesis2; There is no difference between the mean scores of post-test between two groups of students in psychological concept. The hypotheses were tested at $P < 0.01$ level of significance

Table:2

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Calculated-t-Value
Group-1	30	31.98	6.97	15.56
Group-2	30	22.98	3.18	0.19

Table-2 reveals that the 't' value is significant at 0.01 level. Hence, it is inferred that there is a significant difference between the two groups as indicated by the mean value which showed that the group-1 better in the achievement test than the students of the group-2. This result obviously showed that learning with the help of video package increased the achievement of the students [g-1]

Hypothesis3: There is no difference between the mean scores of experimental group students in psychological concept. The hypotheses were tested at $P < 0.01$ level of significance.

Table:3

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Calculated-t-Value
Pre-test	30	22.30	3.15	21.55
Post-test	30	31.98	4.98	0.19

Table -3 reveals that the 't' value is significant at 0.01 level. Hence, it is inferred that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement test scores of the pre -test and post - test for the group-1. The higher mean value in the post test shows that the students fared better in the post -test than in the pre-test. This result obviously showed that learning with the help of multimedia package profusely increased the achievement of the students [g-1] Hypothesis4; There is no difference between the mean scores of control

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group students in psychological concept. The hypotheses were tested at $P < 0.05$ level of significance.

Table-4

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Calculated-t-Value
Pre-test	30	19.89	1.98	0.057
Post-test	30	22.98	2.38	0.19

Table-4 Indicates that the 't' value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, it is inferred that there no significant difference between the mean achievement test scores of the pre -test and that of the post - test for the control group. This result obviously showed that learning with the traditional method meagrely increased the achievement of the students [g-2]

Findings

There is no significant difference between the group-1 and the group-2 in the learning of psychological concept at the pre-test level. There is a significant difference between the group-1 and the group-2 in the learning of psychological concept at the post-test level. There is a significant difference between the mean achievement test score of the pre-test and post-test for the group-,1 There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test for the pre-test and post-test for the group-2.

Conclusion

Findings of the study showed that the students learning through multimedia package have impact on learning of psychological concept. The developed interactive multimedia package is practical to be used and implemented because it attracts student's attention and participates in the learning process. The use of interactive multimedia in the learning process can also improve student's learning outcomes and effective to be used as guidance for teachers and students. ICT and media are an asset that have to be integrated in the practices and instructional strategies, as they are facilitating tools that encourage creativity and autonomy, have a great potential for motivation, promote networking and information sharing, and last but not the least contribute, by young people, for the appropriation of technological literacy and skills that will allow them to integrate the information and knowledge society.

References

- [1] Driscoll, Tom. (2012), Flipped learning and democratic Education; The complete Report retrieve from [http:// www.flipped-histry.com/2012/12/ flipped -learning-democratic-education.html](http://www.flipped-histry.com/2012/12/flipped-learning-democratic-education.html)
- [2] FloralJeya & Saravanakumar(2018) "Flipped Classroom-SWOC Analysis." Review of Research International on-line Multidisciplinary Journal, August 2018, Vol:07, issue:11 p1-4, ISSN:2249-894X, Impact Factor:5.76311 FloralJeya.S& Saravanakumar.AR.[2022], "Perceptual Understanding Of Psychological Learning For Memory And Retention In Education, 'International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research, Volume 9, Issue3[1], ISSN2394-778
- [3] FloralJeya.S & Saravanakumar. AR [2022], "Application Of Multimedia Elements In A Flipped Classroom, Journal Of Education, Vol XXIV No;[X]ISSN;0972-7175
- [4] Floral Jeya.S & Saravanakumar. AR [2022], "Multimedia Technology and Impact on Physical Education." In the 3rd International Conference On "Emerging Challenges in Physical Education. TamilNadu Teacher Education University, Chennai. 2022

THE HOLISTIC ANALYSIS OF MULTICULTURAL TEACHING

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Abstract

Holistic education is a comprehensive approach in teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. Multicultural education is a modern teaching model that aims to foster principles of equity amongst all students despite their varied cultures, ethnicities, races, beliefs, and backgrounds. It is an effective form of education that integrates the values, histories, and viewpoints of all student groups in a class. India is multicultural and emerging globalized society. Indian culture is the culture of diversity. Indian education system needs secular and democratic value based. So it is not a particular culture but mixture of various cultures. To transmit this culture from generation to generation, the role of education is very important. Multicultural education acts as a way for students from different cultural groups to communicate and interact with each other. The purpose of this paper is to introduce people to multicultural education and to establish a global society in which people of different religion, different caste and different socio- economic status are involved.

Keywords: *Holistic Education, Globalized Society, Educational Equity, Social Justice.*

Introduction

Multicultural education is a set of educational strategies developed to provide students with knowledge about the histories, cultures, and contributions of diverse groups. It draws on insights from multiple fields, reinterprets content from related academic disciplines. It is a way of teaching that promotes the principles of inclusion, democracy, skill acquisition, inquiry, critical thinking, multiple perspectives, and self-reflection.

Objectives

The objectives of multicultural education vary among educational philosophers and political theorists. Educational philosophers argue for preservation of minority cultures by fostering students' development of autonomy and introducing them to multiple cultures. This exposure assists students in thinking more critically, as well as, encourages them to have a more open mindset. Teachers then serve as change agents, promoting relevant democratic values and empowering students to act.

Other Goals Include

- 1) Promote civic good.
- 2) Correct historical records.
- 3) Increase student self-esteem.
- 4) Diversify student exposure.
- 5) Preserve minority group culture.
- 6) Foster student autonomy.
- 7) Promote social justice.
- 8) Enable students to succeed economically.

Multicultural in Education

Multicultural education is a modern teaching model. From language barriers to social skills, behaviour to discipline, and classroom involvement to academic performance, multicultural education aims to provide equitable educational opportunities to all students. Furthermore, it is a set of teaching strategies formed to help guide a teacher to remove barriers faced in a multicultural class. It also helps teachers respond to the issues faced by diverse students and eliminate them. A multicultural teacher hence accepts the differences, identifies the negativity, and is always conscious to procure the cultural identity of all the students.

Why Do we Need a Multicultural Curriculum?

Multicultural education is highly focused on bringing together students from all backgrounds and promoting collaborative learning. However, there are many more reasons to implement a multicultural curriculum in our classroom.

- 1) A multicultural curriculum exposes students to various cultural values through activities, lectures, discussions, etc.
- 2) It allows students to identify cultural as well as physical differences.

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- 3) It also develops a sense of respect amongst classmates.
- 4) Implementing a multicultural curriculum at a young age nurtures students to reflect on their cultural diversity with pride.
- 5) It implants patience, liberalism, and individualism in students.
- 6) It fosters friendships, encourages interaction, and improves communication skills.

Implementation of Multicultural Education in the Classroom

- 1) To Understand the Students.
- 2) To Identify Strengths and Weaknesses of the students.
- 3) To Encourage Real-Life Experiences.
- 4) To Organize Open Discussions.
- 5) To Plan Group Activities.
- 6) To Cultural Food Swap.
- 7) To Encourage Cultural Storytelling.
- 8) To Hold Multicultural Seminars & Events.
- 9) To Schedule a Monthly Culture Day.
- 10) To Celebrate Native Festivals.

Advantages of Multicultural Classroom

Education is the successful and powerful tool to make the nation globalized society. In an ever-changing global scenario, it has become imperative to equip students with adequate exposure to be citizens of the future.

Exposes Students to Different Cultures

Students belonging to different religions get to know about different customs, festivals and living habits and also participate in all of them without any discrimination. Multicultural education acts as a way for students from different cultural groups to communicate and interact with each other.

Fosters Acceptance and Tolerance in a Learning Environment

A multicultural education provides educational opportunities to learners from diverse ethnic cultural groups and social classes. It enables students to acquire skills and develop a positive attitude.

Teaches Multiple Perspectives

The multicultural classroom provides an opportunity for students from different cultures to bring their enormous range of experiences, knowledge, perspectives and insights to the classroom.

Help to Build an International Network

Multicultural education increases positive relationships through achievement of common goals, respect, appreciation, and commitment to equality among the intellectuals at institutions of higher education.

Conclusion

This paper tells about multicultural education and effective teaching strategies that can be used in the classroom. It highly focuses on bringing together students from all backgrounds and promoting collaborative learning. Also, helps teachers interact with students from different cultures that accelerate the professional growth of a teacher. For the development of the globalized society, multicultural education must be included in the education from primary level to higher level so that the entire global society can move ahead on the path of progress by rising above the discrimination of castes, religions, races and languages.

References

- [1] Banks, J. A. (1995a). Multicultural Education: Historical Development, Dimensions, and Practice. In J. A. Banks & C. A. M. Banks (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on Multicultural Education* (pp. 3-24). New York: Macmillan.
- [2] Banks, J. A. (1999). *An Introduction to Multicultural Education* (2nd edition).
- [3] Boston: Allyn and Bacon. Banks, J. (1997). *Educating Citizens in a Multicultural Society*. Teachers College Press: New York and London.
- [4] Dogan, C. (2017). The Importance of Multiculturalism in Community Interpreting. *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*. 07(02), pp 72-77.
- [5] Eruz, S. (2010). *Multiculturalism and Translation*. Multilingual Publishing, Istanbul.
- [6] Islam, H. M., (2021). Nature of Multicultural Education Curriculum. *Kariman*, 09(01), pp 49-68.

CHANGING CONTOURS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND YOGA -AN EDUCATION CONTINUUM: ISSUES AND INTRICACIES

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Abstract

The National Education Policy 2020 was approved by the Union Cabinet in July. It seeks to reform the education system of India and overarches the structural issues in the present Education System. The National Education Policy 2020 strongly emphasizes including sports and physical education as a part of the curriculum. It is recognized as a subject to be taught and the physical aspects are limited to physical education sessions. The idea is not much different from what already exists. The policy merely makes it mandatory what was otherwise an option in many schools. The present article throws light on the significance of physical education and sports across the levels of education-pre-primary, primary, secondary, higher secondary, and higher education. The views provide an array of pertinence in the realm of all-round development of an individual. Health is wealth-goes the old saying. The head, heart and soul reside in a body and physical education and yoga provides a sound health of all these. The position of physical education, yoga and sports in all levels of educational curricula can sign a positive and confident youth, who could contribute to the development of the nation. The NEP 2020 thus envisaged the inclusion of physical education, sports, yoga and mental health in the educational contours, augmenting their existing position in the respective curricula.

Keywords: *Physical Education, Yoga, Sports, NEP 2020*

Educational Significance Overture

The word 'Education' is derived from the Latin word 'Educatum', which means to bring out. The meaning of education is 'to bring out the best qualities of the individual'. Education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, morals, beliefs and habits. According to Swami Vivekananda, Education is the manifestation of the perfection already in humans. It is a well-established scientific fact that Physical inactivity is a key determinant of health across the lifespan. Physical education and a variety of sports are essential for the mental and physical development of the students. Sports help in better development of children and side by side it helps in character building and psychological training of students. Sports and Physical education build the personality and develops many life's skills for children. Team sports or individual games, be it indoor or outdoor-contribute largely to this multi-faceted development. At present a child is being entirely deprived of this experience- and this seriously impacts his/her personality. The Revelation: Physical Education is a very wide subject in which biological, psychological, physical, health and functional aspects of sports and body are studied. It is noteworthy that it is such a subject with the help of which human body both internally and externally can be kept healthy. Students will definitely be able to discharge duties towards themselves and society through this subject. Under this subject, the students can demonstrate excellently their skills and perfection particularly in sports ability, management, leadership, health plan, event management, sports budgeting, physiology, teaching methods, sports psychology and research along with getting information regarding to the importance of Physical Education for DIVYANG-adapted physical education and sports. We have to prepare the citizens of 21st Century equipped with Critical Thinking, Problem Solving, Analytic Reasoning, Cognitive Skills, and Self-Directed Learning etc. Under the new system, sports will become a part-and- parcel of the school education system. The sports curriculum will be designed, depending on the infrastructure in the school campus and may also be shared from the neighboring campuses.

The Pedagogical Tenets: The Main Goals in Teaching Modern Physical Education are (NCBI, 2013)

- 1) To expose children and teens to a wide variety of exercise and healthy activities.
- 2) To teach skills to maintain a lifetime of fitness as well as health.
- 3) To encourage self-reporting and monitoring of exercise.
- 4) To individualize duration, intensity, and type of activity.
- 5) To focus feedback on the work, rather than the result.
- 6) To provide active role models.

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It is critical for physical educators to foster and strengthen developing motor skills and to provide children and teens with a basic skill set that builds their movement repertoire, which allows students to engage in various forms of games, sports, and other physical activities throughout their lifetime. These goals can be achieved in a variety of ways. National, state, and local guidelines often dictate which standards must be taught in regards to physical education. These standards determine what content is covered, the qualifications educators must meet, and the textbooks and materials which must be used. These various standards include teaching sports education, or the use of sports as exercise; fitness education, relating to overall health and fitness; and movement education, which deals with movement in a non- sport context (Kun, 2003).

The Necessity

Extrapolating the words of Swami Jib, the paradigms of Physical Education, Sports and Yoga are integrated under the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. Physical Education, Sports and Yoga professionals, will contribute infringing Health and Wellness at every aspect of one's personality. Thus, developing and proposing the syllabus framework for Physical Education, Sports and Yoga is a precedence of all levels of educational institutions. In this context, the Physical Education, Sports and Yoga professionals, will contribute in bringing Health and Wellness at every aspect of an individual's personality.

NEP Contouring the Education Scenario

The vision of India's new education system has accordingly been crafted tonsure that it touches the life of each and every citizen. The new National Education Policy has brought vicissitudes in this regard. At this juncture when the health, happiness and immunity of children are becoming increasingly important due to the coved pandemic, NEP has been a sunup for all education seekers. The new NEP-2020 includes several key points that are instrumental for the holistic development of a child. By eliminating the rigid separation between curricular and extra-curricular activities, the NEP-2020 acknowledges sports to be equally important as any other subject like English or Science, thereby increasing the Fun and Engagement that children desperately seek in a school. Another reform on Vocational Education is also great step towards all-round development of children. Physical Activity and Sports will be offered as a Vocational subject. The students will be encouraged to choose these vocational subjects. It is noticed that every child enjoys a certain type of sports or have hobbies of games and or any particular physical activity. It is undeniably witnessed that children/students tend to perform better in subjects or curriculum they love to do.

The Prospects of Sports Education

Sports education builds the personality and develops many life skills for children. Team sports or individual games, be it indoor or outdoor- contribute largely to this multi-faceted development. Now imagine, a child being entirely deprived of this experience- how does it impact one's personality? Best sports schools in West Bengal recognize this gap and hence have developed a sports-centric flexible curriculum. Here, academics and sports are equally prioritized and extraordinary talents are recognized and nurtured from an early stage. Being a part of a sports school, children get the scope to find out their calling in specific types of sports while trying out different options. At the sometime, their academics do not get neglected. But more than anything, the child has an overall physical and mental development that brings out the best anthem as an adult later in life.

End Thoughts

The value of embracing a physically active lifestyle has been well documented since long and is highly pronounced in recent times. But it is noted that despite of this knowledge, physical activity levels remain exorbitantly lowing children and youth-one is the precursor, whilst the other is the nation builder. Habit formation in youth is a key indicator of engagement in physical activity as an adult; therefore, maximizing opportunities to develop motivation in young people is indispensably imperative to escalate the likelihood of maintaining physical activity habits as an adult. A key factor for the development of motivation is school-based physical education (Winkle, 2022). This article portrays the contours of physical education, sports and yoga as media for physical activity promotion, and suggests that a change of approach that moves with the motion of NEP 2020 across curricula in education continuum.

References

- [1] Approaches to Physical Education in Schools. NCBI. 30 October 2013.
- [2] Paula Keyes Kun (December 30, 2003). "Children Need Greater Amount of Physical Activity in 2004" (PDF). National Association for Sport and Physical Education.
- [3] <https://www.financialexpress.com/education-2/nep-2020-envisages-sports-as-part-of-curriculum-says-dharmendra-pradhan/2648948/>. Retrieved on 25/11/2022

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DIVULGING THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN PROMOTING MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

India is a multi-cultural country where different people stay together harmoniously by respecting different cultures, food habits, dress codes, religions, etc. The cultural diversity of India has been marked by its long history, geography and diverse demography. It encourages open-mindedness amongst different groups of people and it eliminates negative stereotypes. Multi-cultural education promotes equal educational opportunities for all students, which includes people from different racial, ethnic and social class groups. This kind of education values the different culture of students and mould them to lead a balanced life in a diverse world. It emphasizes equality, justice and equity more and opens the window to the world of reality in classrooms. A teacher can promote multicultural education by selecting and managing policies, curricula and teaching styles which value and respect all cultural diversities prevailing in society. A teacher has to play diverse roles like that of a planner, facilitator, co-creator of knowledge, leader in the classroom and outside the classroom, manager, and counsellor and above all, he/she should be a true human being who can understand and cope with the diversities.

Keywords: *Teachers, Promoting, Multicultural Education, Cultural Diversities*

Introduction

In the words of Kofi Annan, “We may have different religions, different languages, different coloured skin, but we all belong to one human race”. Multicultural education paves the way for better opportunities for learning especially for the marginalized community who is oppressed by their skin colour or where they come from. The main aim is to promote educational, economic and social equity among all. All the teachers should act as a catalyst to develop a positive attitude to communicate and interact with others, thereby showing acceptance and tolerance towards other cultures and finally resulting in a moral and civic community. The classroom exposure should teach the child how to incorporate or accommodate the histories, values, beliefs and perspectives of people from other cultural backgrounds. There should be rich content integration and the knowledge-constructing process should enhance the equity pedagogy thereby giving some awareness about other cultures too. This progressive approach transforms education based on equality and social justice. Both the teachers and students should inculcate an inclusive approach to the views and contributions of diverse people to assimilate them into the mainstream or dominant culture.

Components of Multicultural Education

- 1) Integrating culturally rich content
- 2) Knowledge and construction process
- 3) Minimizing the prejudice
- 4) Equity in pedagogy

Integrating Culturally Rich Content

Teachers play a vital role in integrating the content by using examples from various cultures and groups. It provides educators with an opportunity to expose students to a variety of cultures. The curriculum board should frame content that clearly and deeply depicts cultural diversity and the need of getting recognition and respect from others. The content should promote the critical thinking of students in a way to include all without any discrimination.

Knowledge and Construction Process

The dissemination of knowledge helps the students to construct and reflect on the experiences imbibed through learning. Teachers should promote awareness among the children about the diversity in the world and why all those diversities should be unified as a single entity. The knowledge construction process aids the students to understand, investigate and learn the biases prevailing in society and thereby minimizing or eradicating the gaps between the mainstream and unknown cultures. Every piece of knowledge should promote wisdom to recognize what is wrong and right and to act diligently without any inequalities.

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Minimizing the Prejudice

Children come to school with a lot of negative attitudes and misconceptions that deviates their thoughts and perspectives into weird one. This includes unwanted notions about racial and ethnic groups that were injected knowingly or unknowingly by our society. These prejudices should be changed at the grass root level itself, only then we can inculcate a good individual who could promote inclusive education and enhances diverse thoughts. The ultimate aim is to create a society that recognizes and respects the culture of diverse people.

Equity in Pedagogy

The term equity means fairness and justice in doing a thing and pedagogy implies the science or art of teaching. We need to acknowledge and make adjustments to all imbalances. For that, the teacher should modify their teaching in a way that aids in the academic achievement of students from diverse cultures, races and social-class groups. Equity pedagogy will help teachers in developing teaching strategies that support the classroom environment, especially for the disadvantaged community inside and outside the campus. Only a well- proficient and competent teacher can alter their teaching to achieve cultural and societal goals.

Role of Teacher

- 1) Be a facilitator who can bridge the gap and link culturally diverse people.
- 2) Promoting learning environment and experience through educational equity.
- 3) Should have integrity and truthfulness, to aspire and influence their students.
- 4) Should be aware of the practices and beliefs of the cultures of their students.
- 5) Should be empathetic and understand the perspectives of the learners.
- 6) Should be flexible in thought and have an open mind to accommodate all.
- 7) Should be a role model in reverence and embracing the multicultural aspects.
- 8) Promoting mushroom growth by accepting and accommodating diversities.
- 9) Providing culturally rich content in their learning activities.
- 10) Promoting a positive attitude towards other cultures and including all without any bias.

Recommendations

The teachers should be well aware of the vitality and need for multicultural education, especially during this twenty-first century and it should be explained how the teachers can impart multicultural education to their students. Teachers should improve the student's cultural and ethnic awareness in order to widen their perspectives and to have more insights about other existing cultures. Teachers should take special care to encourage the students to accept other cultures and avoid biased assimilation. Multicultural education is very useful to assimilate and understand new cultural diversities prevailing in our society. Providing a culturally rich environment and content can change the students' attitudes and perceptions in accommodating other subcultures.

Conclusion

A teacher plays a crucial role in the achievement of each learner in the classroom. This responsibility rises to its pinnacle with the assistance of multicultural classrooms. A conscientious teacher should have empathy, sensitivity to culture, a broad mind, and a strong sense of integrity. Only then they can transform their students with humane values, thereby making him/her utilitarian product for society. In short, multicultural education supports equality in considering ethnic diversities in classrooms and incorporating them into lesson plans and learning activities, thereby making the learning process more fruitful with humane values. Thus, the subcultures can move forward along with the mainstream culture with due respect and acceptance by all.

References

- [1] Brandt, J. (2007). Understanding and dismantling racism: The twenty-first century challenge to white America. Fortress Press.
- [2] Coombe, Rachel. Teaching in multicultural classrooms: tips, challenges and opportunities. 7 November, 2012. The Guardian. Teacher Blog. Web.<https://www.theguardian.com/teacher-network/teacher-blog/2012/nov/07/teaching-multicultural-classroom-advice-challenges>
- [3] Health of children. (2012). Multicultural education& curriculum. (2012). Retrieved from <http://www.healthofchildren.com/M/Multicultural-Education-Curriculum.html>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

A STUDY EXPLORING THE NEED OF RAMP DESIGN FEATURE IN ELDERLY HOUSING

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Abstract

In many industrialized nations, about one in five of the population age is over 65, reflecting an ageing global population. Gradual changes in vision, hearing, balance, coordination, and memory occur as people get older. To satisfy the needs of individuals of all ages, products, communication tools, and the physical environment must be thoughtfully developed. The current study investigated the difference between ramp design and housing demands for elderly people. The older women (n=60) who could complete their daily tasks and were at least sixty years old were chosen as a sample. The Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh served as the location of the sample. The standard design guidelines, which were developed through study by numerous government and non-government organisations, provided as a benchmark for identifying the characteristics existing and the requirements for ramp design in senior housing. The findings showed that the majority of elderly respondents (93.33%) had a neutral opinion regarding ramp provision. A lesser percentage (6.67%) had favoured the provision of ramps in accordance with the regulations. The specifications for a ramp include its width, length, and the presence of railings to facilitate easier movement for elderly people. The Chi-square value was found to be significant. This is good evidence that the null hypothesis is incorrect. As a result, there is a connection between the current ramp design and the respondents' needs to age in place in terms of ramp design. The study's sample of existing homes found that ramps were not particularly popular.

Keywords: *Ramp, Elderly People, Safety, Housing*

Introduction

There will be a rapid growth in the number of older people worldwide by 2050 (United Nations 2020). As a result of the substantial increase in life expectancy in recent years, a greater number of elderly persons may now experience later-life ill health and impairment. Ramps are sloping walkways that can be found inside or outside of buildings and are used to give access between floors. For persons in wheelchairs and those with mobility challenges, ramps offer an alternative to stairs. Ramps are essential for elderly home safety so that they can leave the house swiftly and safely in an emergency. Older individuals can live more responsibly and with better quality of life if they remain independent. They can maintain their freedom by having ramps installed where they are required. Ramps might enable older individuals to remain in a house and neighbourhood that they like. Elderly persons will be kept safe by improvements like grab bars, additional lighting, and wheel chair ramps (www.aipmobilityplus.com/wheel-chair-ramps-for-the-elderly). According to a study on the usage of stairs and ramps, older persons preferred ramps over stairs since they had better balance, had less tripping, and felt more comfortable. (Wolfenbarger, 2001). The ability to see well is crucial for movement. Due to their difficulty spotting stair edges, people with poor vision prefer ramps for descent (Simoneau, 1991). Ramps provide older persons with a safer way to move around because they account for the changes in balance and mobility that come with age. Parkinson's disease patients, who are more likely to have declines in their cognitive and physical capacities, can also employ the safer means of transportation. The study's goal was to investigate the mismatch between current ramp designs and the needs of senior citizens living in homes.

Methodology

The Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh was the location of the study. For the study, an ex-post-facto research design was used. The places from which the sample will be drawn were chosen using a random sampling procedure. The sample was taken using the purposeful sampling technique from the randomly chosen study areas. The selection criteria were 60 elderly women aged 60 and older who could manage their daily tasks alone and lived in a separate house without children with or without a spouse. The standard design principles, which were developed as a result of study by various government and non-government organisations and researchers, served as a benchmark for determining the features and requirements of the aged. The information was gathered using a schedule of organised interviews and observations. Elderly homes chosen for the study were physically examined, information on housing provisions was acquired, and the residences were scored 3, 2, and 1 for being above recommended guidelines, exactly as recommended guidelines, and below recommended guidelines. The respondents were asked about their suggestions for ramp design that would allow them to age comfortably and freely while taking into account their constraints. With scores of 3, 2, and 1, respectively, the needs of the elderly were classified as neutral, essential, and preferred. For the respondents' needs and the current ramp design, frequencies and percentages were computed. Chi

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square analysis was used to determine the disconnect between the respondent's needs and the current ramp design in the houses.

Standard Design Guidelines for Ramp Design

Guidelines for provision of Ramp design in the home were gathered through literature survey. served as a base for identifying the features to measure the existing ramp design in the house .According to Central Public Works Department (1998) ramp should be finished with non-slip material. Minimum width of ramp should be 6 feet with maximum gradient 1:12, length of ramp should not exceed 29 feet 6 inches having double handrail at a height of 3 feet on both sides. Minimum gap from the adjacent wall to the hand rail should be 1.9 inch. Provision of steep ramps should be avoided. According to Model guidelines for development and regulation of retirement homes (2019) Ramps should be provided throughout the building to provide for easy access for elderly people and wheelchair users. According to National Building Code (2016) the landing should be provided at the bottom and the top of a sloped path, a stepped path, or a ramp and also where the run changes direction. The length of an end landing and an in-between landing should be not less than 5 feet. Where the ramp run changes direction, the minimum landing dimensions should be not less than 5 feet by 5 feet. The area of a landing shall be clear of any obstruction including the path of swing of a door or a gate.

Results and Discussion

Existing Ramp Design in Elderly People Housing

Six standard design guidelines were identified to assess the design of ramp in elderly housing. Majority (98%) of the houses had no minimum ramp width and length as per the guidelines. Maximum ramps were provided with non-slip floor material and with no flat slope and also not provided with handrails at proper height as per the recommended guidelines.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by existing ramp design features

Recommended Design Guidelines	Status of existing design features against the guidelines						Total	
	Above the recommended guidelines		Exactly as per the recommended guidelines		Below the recommended guidelines		N	%
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Minimum width of ramp was 6 feet with maximum gradient 1:12	0	0	1	1.67	59	98.33	60	100
Ramp was finished with non-slip floor material	4	6.67	0	0	56	93.33	60	100
Length of ramp was not exceed higher than 29 feet 6 inches	0	0	0	0	60	100	60	100
Ramp had double handrail at a height of 2 feet 7 inches to 3 feet	0	0	3	5	57	95	60	100
Ramps with flat slope were present	3	5	1	1.67	56	93.33	60	100
No steep ramps were installed	4	6.67	0	0	56	93.33	60	100

Ramp were provided near the entrance to facilitate wheel chair or a vehicle to drive in. Ramps in place of steps or staircase were not familiar in existing houses.

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Needs of Elderly People in Ramp Feature

The respondents were asked to state their recommendations to design ramp to enable them to live comfortably in old age keeping in view of their limitations. All most the total respondents expressed neutral view towards the provision of ramps with reference to minimum width (98%) and length (93 %), non-slip floor material (98%), ramp with flat slope (95%) and avoid steep ramps (91%). All the respondents felt neutral towards the provision of handrails to the ramps.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents by their needs in designing a ramp

Housing Needs of the Elderly	Adequacy of housing needs						Total	
	Essential		Preferred		Neutral			
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Minimum width of ramp is 6 feet with maximum gradient 1:12	1	1.67	0	0	59	98.33	60	100
Ramp should be finished with non-Slippery floor material	0	0	2	3.33	58	96.67	60	100
Length of ramp shall not exceed higher than 29 feet 6 inches	4	6.67	0	0	56	93.33	60	100
Ramp should have double handrail at a height of 2 feet 7 inches to 3 feet	0	0	0	0	60	100	60	100
Ramps with flat slope are recommended	0	0	3	5	57	95	60	100
Avoid the installation of steep ramps	5	8.33	0	0	55	91.67	60	100

Elderly respondents felt it was essential to avoid the installation of steep ramps and limit the length of ramp no higher than 29 feet 6 inches. Mostly the elderly had not expressed a firm view in the design of ramp. Association between existing design features of ramp and needs of the elderly. Chi square analysis was done to find out the association between existing ramp design and needs of the elderly people. The null hypothesis formulated was H_0 1 There exists no significant association between existing ramp design and needs of elderly with reference to ramp design to age in place. Majority (93.33%) of the elderly felt neutral for the provision of ramps. Negotiable proportion (6.67%) had preferred for the provision of ramps as per the guidelines.

Table 3. Association between existing design features of ramp and needs of the elderly

Existing Ramp features	Design needs with reference to ramp					
	Neutral		Preferred		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Below the recommended guidelines	56	93.33	0	0.00	56	93.33
As per the recommended guidelines	0	0.00	4	6.67	4	6.67
Total	56	93.33	4	6.67	60	100.00
χ^2 value	60					
Probability value	<.0001*					

The Chi-square value (0.0001) was found to be highly significant. This is a strong evidence against the null hypothesis. Hence, null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is an association between the existing ramp design and the needs of the respondents to age in place with reference to ramp design.

Conclusion

It was concluded that for persons in wheelchairs and those with mobility challenges, ramps offer an alternative to stairs. Ramps are essential for elderly home safety so that they can leave the house swiftly and safely in an emergency. With regard to minimum ramp width (98%) and length (93%), non-slip floor material (98%), ramp with flat slope (95%) and avoid steep ramps (91%), the vast majority of respondents expressed a neutral response. Regarding the addition of railings to the ramps, every responder had an unfavorable opinion. The majority of older people (93.33%) had a neutral opinion regarding ramp provision. A lesser percentage (6.67%) had favoured the provision of ramps in accordance with the regulations. The specifications for a ramp include its width, length, and the presence of railings to facilitate easy movement for elderly people.

References

- [1] Wolfenbarger, K. G., & Shehab, R. L. (2000, July). A survey of ramp and stair use among older adults. In Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting (Vol. 44, No. 24, pp. 4-76). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications.
- [2] Simoneau, G. G., Cavanagh, P. R., Ulbrecht, J. S., Leibowitz, H. W., & Tyrrell, R. A. (1991). The influence of visual factors on fall-related kinematic variables during stair descent by older women. *Journal of gerontology*, 46(6), M188-M195.
- [3] United Nations. 2020. World Population Ageing 2019(ST/ESA/SER.A/444). New York. <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/pdf/ageing/WorldPopulationAgeing2019-Report.pdf>.
- [4] National building code. 2016. Requirements for accessibility in built environment for elders and persons with disabilities. Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi. 1:49-136. <https://standardsbis.bsbedge.com/>
- [5] Model Guidelines for Development and Regulations of Retirement homes. 2019. Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India. <http://mohua.gov.in/upload/uploadfiles/files/Retirement%20Model%20Guidelines%20Book.pdf>
- [6] Central Public Works Department .1998. Guidelines and Space Standards for Barrier Free Built Environment for Disabled and Elderly Persons. 1998. <https://cpwd.gov.in/Publication/aged&disabled.PDF>
- [7] <https://www.aipmobilityplus.com/wheel-chair-ramps-for-the-elderly/> accessed on 22/1/2023.

IMPROVING OUTCOMES IN EDUCATION BY USING SELFEVALUATION

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Abstract

Assessment and Evaluation are two important cornerstones of teaching and learning but these are seldom focused upon with respect to Self Evaluation . The paradox is that we often use these terminologies only in the context of learners and our lens is restricted to cover mostly just the cognitive domain .We easily or intentionally forget about the affective and the psychomotor domains of learning, thus deeming them to be of less value. In this technology enabled and technologically driven century wherein the learners have an easy access to information, isn't it important to look beyond the cognitive aspects and rather strengthen the assessment and evaluation procedures so that we are able to know how well our education system is attuned to cater to the affective and psychomotor domains of the tender minds. We also need to focus on the teacher education institutions so as to see if these are equipping the teachers of tomorrow in a way that they are able to engage in critical thinking and reflection in order to evaluate their own self before they evaluate their students. The present paper discusses the role of self evaluation for improving the outcomes of education.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking; Reflection; Outcome Based Education*

Need for Self Evaluation

All across the world you see policy makers and administrators shifting the focus to outcomes rather than output with respect to education. We ,as teachers and teacher educators, too are worried as to how to ensure that our students learn meaningfully and joyfully such that they attain the desired milestones with respect to knowledge ,attitudes and skills. Once this takes place the student will easily find a firm and desired place in the world of work too and contribute effectively in the development of a healthy and vibrant democratic space everywhere. One of the most important factors which facilitates the holistic development of the pupil in every possible way is undoubtedly the teacher .For the teacher to be effective one of the most important aspects to be considered is whether the teacher reflect on his/her practices .A teacher's journey never reaches close to perfection unless he/she continuously strives to reinvent himself/herself in the light of the feedback of his/her peers and students. This journey begins with self evaluation of one's own practices which may be done by personal reflection or by seeking formal assessment .Self evaluation not only supports the teacher to improve the classroom experiences of learners but also helps him/her to recognize the need for capacity building in the identified areas. In the present day classrooms, more emphasis is being laid upon adopting constructivist pedagogies so that the students take ownership of their own learning as teachers and students venture into learning with each other . The present day classrooms favoring collaborative learning and cooperative learning definitely require the methods of assessment which measure beyond the cognitive domain of the students and therefore peer Assessment and self assessment are the core focal areas to be looked into. The terms "assessment" and "evaluation" are related, as the value judgments when added to assessment becomes evaluation. Self evaluation is required to understand one's strengths and weaknesses; find out the ways to improve and know what needs to be done to achieve the next goal. Undoubtedly meta-cognition plays a big role in self evaluation. Self-evaluation is often very desirable as a means of enhancing personal development and for the growth of an organization. In the context of Teaching – Learning, self evaluation manifests at three levels:

Student Self Evaluation

Self Evaluation by the student is very important as it helps the learner know not only about their learning achievements but also about their learning experiences. It helps the student take charge of its own learning because self evaluation help the child know and express what 'he /she can'/or has achieved and what 'he/she is not able to'. National Curriculum Framework 2005 states that

“Every classroom interaction with children requires their evaluation of their own work, and a discussion with them about what should be tested and the ways of finding out whether the competencies are being developed or not”. – (NCF2005, p75)

Student Self Evaluation helps the student to:

- 1) Know their strengths
- 2) Identify the areas where they are lagging behind
- 3) Set realistic goals
- 4) Plan for revisions
- 5) Track their own progress

Student Self Evaluation helps the students stay motivated and be responsible for their own learning.

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Student Self Evaluation is valuable for teachers as well because it helps them understand the child in a much better way and implement pedagogies that cater to the individual needs and learning styles. NCF 2005 advocates that Self Assessment by the student must form a part of the summative evaluation as well. It says :

“Along with the teacher assessing each child, each student could also assess himself or herself and include this self assessment in the report card”. – (NCF2005, p76)

Teacher Self Evaluation

Teacher Self Evaluation is essential as it not only helps teachers enhance their professional competencies and stay abreast of the latest developments but also enables them to ascertain how the various factors (personal/institutional) impact their teaching. Teacher Self Evaluation helps strengthen not merely the teaching competencies but also the classroom management skills so that it leads to effective teaching. Teacher Self Evaluation helps the teachers to monitor and adjust instruction so that it maximizes students’ learning in the given conditions with the available resources. Critical evaluation of teaching strategies and instructional techniques by the teacher himself /herself helps to evolve and become effective teachers.

Teacher Self Evaluation helps the teacher to:

- 1) Relook and Re-align teaching and classroom management strategies
- 2) Refine their teaching skills
- 3) Develop better Interpersonal Relationships
- 4) Find out ways to maximize learning outcomes
- 5) Create enriched teaching-learning environments
- 6) Identify professional development programs for improving their own performance
- 7) Document Best Practices
- 8) Prepare themselves for Professional Development

Buchanan and Jackson(1998) report that self evaluation led to the development of competence and confidence among the trainee teachers. Majzub (2013) reports that self reflection improves self esteem and teaching competencies of trainee teachers and also concludes that they are able to manage the teaching climate in a better way during teaching practicum. When teachers evaluate their own self, such introspection gives them a deeper understanding and help them change attitudes and behavior. In the book Teacher self-evaluation: Teachers in their own mirror, author Lya Kremer-Hayon (p.131) points out the following areas for teacher self evaluation:

- 1) “The teacher in relation with others - community members, parents, school principal, colleagues, and pupils;
- 2) Teachers’ professional attitudes;
- 3) Teaching experiences, including the varying facets of planning, implementation and evaluation, or viewed from a different angle;
- 4) The school and classroom environment and culture.”

Teachers’ self evaluation may be recorded and analysed in two ways: quantitatively and qualitatively. The various ways to collect data include on Audio/videotapes; Documentation into Journals, logs, diaries and portfolios .The other ways of recording data includes documenting activities, reflections and narratives in detail . The quantitative methods include category systems like the Flanders interaction Analysis, rating scales and check lists. In the book –‘Teachers in their own mirrors’ (p141), author states: “The process of documentation helps to make things clear; it is like talking to oneself without the inhibition that may be aroused by the presence of others. The moment incidents are written down they can be looked at from the distance of an outside observer. After some time they can be re-read and interpreted from richer and additional perspectives, not only because of the time lapse, but also because of teachers' growing experience and knowledge. By analyzing these differences in interpretations teachers are likely to gain more insight into their teaching, become more sensitive observers and aware of their growth.” Based on the above inputs from different social scientists and academicians it is worthwhile to consider documenting the following aspects :

- 1) Focus Group discussions between teachers ,parents, administrators and students;
- 2) Pedagogical and methodological issues and concerns that emerge from reading research in education ;
- 3) Best Practices in Teaching and Research;
- 4) Problems in Implementation of Policy, Innovative Pedagogies, Evaluation techniques etc.

Institutional Self Evaluation

Self Evaluation of the educational institution is important to gauge their performance. It is vital for the improvement and development of the institution. Institutional Self Evaluation is a collaborative, reflective process of review of the institution by the Head and the Faculty in consultation with the Parents and Students. All the stake holders engage in a reflective enquiry on the work of the institution.

Institutional Self Evaluation enables institutions to:

- 1) Improve the quality of education being provided
- 2) Identify areas that need attention
- 3) Communicate their role to the society
- 4) Plan for improvement and expansion

Institutional Self Evaluation can be used for external evaluation and accreditation purposes.

Modern Day Tools for Documentation of Self Evaluation

In this technologically advanced age where the paper and pen have been replaced with kindle, tablets and smart phones, there are many tools available which help us in documentation of self evaluation. A few of them are discussed below: An e -Portfolio (electronic portfolio) can be best defined as a digital compilation of the work of a learner which may include diverse array of works . An E - Portfolio may include :

- 1) Writings (all published and unpublished works)
- 2) Showcasing of all content digitally in the form of audio and video files which may include seminar presentations, research outcomes showcasing etc
- 3) Hyperlinks to the digital content created online which may include links to blogs
- 4) ,social networking web pages etc.

These 'artifacts' may be accompanied by reflection on how or why the item is included in the e-Portfolio in order to support the need for it's creation .

Uses of an e-Portfolio

- 1) e Portfolios provide an outlet for assessment based on looking at the trajectory of an individual's growth over time and does not seal the fate based on a single external examination.
- 2) Artifacts including graphics, stills, multimedia, stories, journals, published works, research projects etc provide a peep into the individual's psyche.
- 3) The collection of works provides a powerful and wide ranging digital platform in the form of a resume that highlights the multiple intelligence of an individual.
- 4) This bioscopic view of a learner's work provides a view of their continuity over a period of time such that the learner can reflect upon the progress, presented as a profile of accomplishment based on documented evidence.

Online Journal keeping: An online learning journal is a collection of notes, anecdotes, observations, thoughts and other relevant reflections recorded over a period of time on an online platform. Maintaining a learning journal enhances the learning through the process of critical thinking and reflecting upon his/her own experiences. Journals can take a number of forms.

Conclusion

Therefore in order to improve are outcomes in terms of knowledge, attitudes and skill sets it is important that self evaluation as a best practice is instituted in every organization be it a school, a college or a university .Care has to be taken that self evaluation is not taken as an exercise to pin individuals down by identifying their weaknesses .It is important that this effective tool is used to improve the performance of students and teachers both, by way of reflection followed by action. There is no doubt that if both the teachers and the students reflect on their own performance based on self evaluation the outcomes in education will automatically improve .Thus there is urgent need for a systemic reform which includes self evaluation as a means for total quality management in education.

References

- [1] An Introduction to School Self-Evaluation of Teaching and Learning in Post-Primary Schools(2012) Inspectorate Department of Education and Skills,Dublin accessed at www.schoolself-evaluation.ie
- [2] Buchanan, D. and Jackson, S.(1998) Supporting Self-Evaluation in Initial Teacher Education. Scottish Educational Review, v30 n2 p110-24 Nov 1998
- [3] Kapur,K.(2008) Assessment for Improving Learning in Schools in India : A perspective available at www.iaea.info/documents/paper_2b71209fa.pdf
- [4] Kremer,L.H.(1993) Teacher Self-Evaluation: Teachers in Their Own Mirrors ,Kulwar Academic Publisher, London.
- [5] Majzub R.(2013) Teacher Trainees' Self Evaluation during Teaching Practicum Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 102 (2013) 195 – 203 retrieved on 30.01.2018 from doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.733

ECONOMIC INCENTIVES SCHEME TOWARDS THE PROTECTION OF GIRL CHILD A:PERCEPTION BASED ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper is structured to analyse the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa to motivate the girl child in the education sector. It also tried to evaluate the perceptions of teachers and guardians regarding this scheme. This descriptive analytical study purposed to establish that if there was a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and guardians and also among the perceptions of different economic class on the impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa. 100 students,50 teachers and 150 guardians was considered as sample. The result of this study shows that, this scheme is very inspiring to promote girl child's education. It reduces the rate of drop out among the school going children and also motivate them to choose higher education. Along with that it significantly increases the marriage age of girl child. Teacher community is generally happy with the positive aspects of this project but there has been disagreement among the parents about this project in light of their financial situation.

Keywords: *Girl Child, Education, Incentives, Motivation, Social Status.*

Introduction

Sustainable protection of the human being has always been a great concern to save the civilization. The term Human Being has a broad sphere to discuss. It includes all the member of the society in terms of their age, gender, physiography and cultural trait. But from the very early period of human civilization, it was found that men hold the prime power to rule the society. Some spurious beliefs about women's subordinate position are there within our society, which are based on cultural and religious concepts that cannot stand up to close scrutiny (Dolphyne, 1991). Men and women, pool and nature, one against the other, diversity of mutual dependence, prosper in cooperation. The dominance of women in matriarchal society and the rule of women in the male dominated society is an escape (Dunga & Mafini,2019). Yet, in India women dignity is recognized. The Vedanta- the Upanishad have placed the women in the seat of honor (Mahapatra,2018). But with the establishment of colony in the Indian sub-continent, women have gradually taken the shelter in the undercover prison. And the practice of screening has begun. Scope of women education, socio-economic power has been dried up (Punam & Sharma, 2017). By the space of time women was considered as the product to the male dominated society. The cruelty of torture is the beginning of the tragedy of this cluster. This hard truth of the society slowly breaks the overall society into some unequal pieces (Equality Now, 2014).In this respect, education of girls offers the new courage for breaking the vicious cycle of feminized deprivation (Summers, 1994). Dolphyne, 1991also added here, only education can provide the proper knowledge to every woman that would expose the stereotypes thought and fallacies behind the cultural practices (Jackson,2009) that keep women in subordination. Rabindranath Tagore wrote about a hundred years ago, "Let women win their own destiny / why god does not provide them that scope?" the answer to this question posed by the poet in the subdued country is still unanswerable. Till today, most of the girls in our society are separated from the main stream of education and are considered as inferior material from the very young age. Still brutal murder or cruelty against girl child, early age marriage (Sen & Ostlin,2007) is widely documented fact in our society (Solotaraff & Pande, 2014). Though the achievement of Bengalis has brought their kingdom forward with much advanced thinking, the path forward for girls is still obstructed. Only a few years ago, West Bengal was considered most top ranked state in the country in early childhood marriage (UNICEF,2018). The rate of drop out among middle school girls was also very high. In order to curb this trend and make women self-reliant, the Government of West Bengal, India launched the social protective scheme for girl child – 'Kanyashree Prakalpa' project in October 27, 2016. Women Development and Social Welfare Authority have taken the responsibility to implement this program under the supervision of Govt. of West Bengal.

Core Elements of the Scheme

The name of the government agency on which the project is being implemented is called "Women Development and Social Welfare, Government of West Bengal" with the prime aim of good for all). But the major concern was –

- 1) Prevalence of infanticide
- 2) Eliminating the practice of early marriage
- 3) To try to ensure that girls can continue their studies up to minimum graduation level.
- 4) Inspire the poor children to continue their education.

To secure the girl children with the above protective measures, several benefits have been thought to be provided to the students in order to constructive development -

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- 1) Unmarried girls from the age of 13 to 18 will get 750 rupees per year to continue their education
- 2) Unmarried girls between the ages of 18 and 19, who enrolled themselves in the higher education institutions, will receive a one-time donation of Rs 25000 from the government. (this is only applicable to the girl who have born after 01/04/1995)

Government of West Bengal has assigned only three eligibility criteria, so that the project can be properly utilized to meet the needs of students –

- 1) The girl child should be unmarried
- 2) The child should not be enrolled under any other scheme of Government.
- 3) There is no economic ceiling to enroll into this scheme.

Nobel winning economist Amartya Sen, in his various writings and in speeches, has repeatedly said that democracy will not become strengthened if inequality is ruin in society. It only happens if, the people who are left behind have taken benefit from development (Sen, 1992). By the twentieth century, women started winning the access to educational program in all level. Feminists from various spheres have made the considerable contributions to spread the gender awareness and empowerment as well as issue related to equal opportunity, access to all the resources such as property (Sultana,2012), wealth and education (Chege & Sifuna, 2006). In the interests of Women's education and progress, the government is thus actively involved and took part in the society, and then every corner of the society feels that inclusiveness. International bodies have also elaborated the same in their various reports.

Objective

The prime objective of this study is to identify the perceptions of different stakeholders about the effectiveness of Kanyashree Prakalpa on girl children.

Methodology

Procedure: To conduct, the whole study, as a first step, a structured questionnaire has been formed. Stratified and Snow-ball sampling method has been applied to collect the data. Data has been collected during November, 2020 to February, 2021. After that, the collected data has been analyzed to understand the trend of the respondent's perception. Participants: The sample consisted of 150 students, 50 female teachers from secondary and higher-secondary level. And 150 guardians from three different levels, respectively on the basis of different economic class (Lower class- below 5000 per month, Middle class- 5000 to 15000 per month, Upper class- More than 15000 per month income. Measures: A structured questionnaire which includes basic information and perception based rating scale was administered on samples. Collected responses have been analyzed through basic descriptive statistics to understand the average responses of the sample. Then t-Test and ANOVA was applied on SPSS 16 to identify the existing differences among the different respondents.

Ho1 - There is no significant difference between the perception of teacher and guardian about the positive aspects of Kanyashree Prakalpa.

Ho2 - There is no significant difference of opinion among the guardians from different economic class regarding the positive impact of Kanyashree Prakalpa.

Analysis and Discussion

In the contemporary world, girl's education has been considered as an important factor for the wide range of developmental indicators including fertility rates, infant mortality ratio, income of family, productive decision making. World Bank economist has also recognized girl's education as single development intervention with the greatest individual and social return (Brent, 2005). Therefore for promoting the girl's education, Kanyashree project has been strongly praised in international platform by UNICEF in the year 2019 as one of the good practice category in Girls Summit, London. This scheme also got 1st place in UNPSA Award, 2017 for its design and features for covering the poorest and the vulnerable groups by an inclusive mechanism. Encouraging the students themselves through the financial support is the core element to this inclusive program. And the concept of 'Student choice construct' has become more relevant in this respect than 'Situational Construct' (CRY, 2019).

Perception of girl Children about this financial support is very positive. They consider that, this scheme has provided them lots of courage to overcome all the obstacles. Annual financial support for the regular students and one time 25,000/- scholarship for the students who get admission in graduation level, make the students more confident and motivating to continue their education without any retention. Henceforth, students also got the support of their parents to study hard to get the scholarship. This scholarship, also provide them material support as the students have to create their own account to receive that fund. So they can use it by their own choice; they usually bought reference book, learning tools like scale, geometric box etc, also expend that fund to enroll them in some courses. Therefore, it is very clear that students becoming so much self-dependent to make their own decisions on the progressive level. Again, this scheme does not come with only financial support, but it also provides the students free coaching on sports, karate,

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yoga etc. this kind of support to promote co-curricular activities also helps the students to broaden their options in the field of higher education.

Shows that 56.67% and 33.33% strongly agree that financial support through kanyashree prakalpa provide them inspiration and also motivate them to peruse higher education where about 4.67% and 3.33% (2 + 1.33) students disagree to the motivational support. 68.67% agree that they receive materialistic support in the form of this financial incentive.

But whenever, the girls' education is considered, the dominating role of the parents is being widely recognized. In this context, the perception about this inspirational incentive (Kanyasree Prakalpa) to promote girl's education among the teacher and guardian has also measured, we have already formed one null hypothesis (Ho) that is- there is no significant difference between the perception of teacher and guardian about the positive aspects of this incentives. To judge this hypothesis, t-test (paired two samples for means) is applied to compare the perceptions of teacher and guardian., responses of teacher and guardian related to every single aspect have been analyzed through Mean and Sd. T-Stat value and p value has also been recorded to judge the hypothesis.

Any kind of economic incentives always considered as the inspirational measures to girl's education. Shows that average response of the teacher (4.3) compare to guardian (4.1) slightly varied in that aspect. Therefore, it is very clear from the p value (0.1049) which is more than $\alpha = 0.05$, indicates that the null hypothesis related to 1st statements is accepted means there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teacher and guardian on the impact of economic support to inspire the children to study hard. So, it can be stated that teacher and parents have expressed equal view that economic incentives for girl children plays an important role to motivate them.

The second statement is hypothetically related to first statement. If the girl child is inspired to study hard from the school level with this financial incentive, then it will plant a remarkable impact on their motivation to pursue higher education. But here the average responses of teacher and guardian are highly varied from each other. Average response of the teacher is 4.625 where for guardian it is 3.275. It clearly denotes that; all parents do not think that this financial incentive can help their children to continue higher education. Respective P value to this statement is 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, means the significant difference is exist between two groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

In most of the developing countries, girl child always considered as burden to their family when compare to son. And they are not getting that much economic support from the family. In this respect, the 3rd statement is implemented that the economic incentive helps the girl child to get equal opportunity. Here the average response of teacher is near 4 (4.025) that means most of the teacher expressed agree to this statement. Whereas, the response of guardian to this statement is comparatively lower (3.325) than the teacher. It is very clear from these two average responses, that parents are not equally agreed to this statement. They have mentioned that, this kind of incentives can be effective for a small period but not justified to sustain the whole life. P value (p is 0.00) of this statement is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

The forth statement also present the same scenario in respect to increase the decision making power of the girl child. Here we have also found the significant different between the response of two group. Most of the teachers are considered it as a progressive tool towards equality whereas guardian's response was below average in this respect.

Drop-out is also considered as one of the concerned issue for girl's education. Most of the girl child from lower to middle economic group has forced to drop their school life because of economic scarcity of their family (Amadi et.al,2013). For instance, in a condition where parents cannot pay fees for both boys and girls, the latter is obvious a detriment, where boys allowed proceeding but girls drop out (Nkinyangi, 1977) (Sultana,2012). So, this kind of constructive economic scheme can provide them some space to continue their education. Here also, the average response of teacher to guardian is varied. Most of the guardian has pointed out to increase the annual scholarship for school child from 700 to 2000 to cover the overall expenses. At the same time guardians have praised the onetime scholarship amount after completing the school education. Although the P value to this statement also 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, means null hypothesis is rejected means there is significant difference between the perception of teacher and guardian.

Girl's age is always considered as a controlling factor to population growth. Whenever any kind of policy is introduced in any country regarding population control, always they put a strong emphasis on marriage age of girl child (Sen & Ostlin,2007). And in this respect, many researchers have found that involvement in formal education can increase the marriage age of girl child. Here, to the 6th statement of the schedule is implemented and to this respect, average response for both the group vary between moderately agree to agree. Average response of the teacher is 3.5 whereas the average response of guardian is 3.2. Therefore, it is very clear that, most of the respondents think, this kind of incentives put moderate impact on society to lose their cognitive blockage about the marriage of girl child. Teachers has also placed the light that, most of the parents think that marriage in early age is very important for girl child (Daraute & Fiske, 2017) and whatever they want to achieve, they should go with the permission of their new family. Here, the P value is 0.0349 (less than $\alpha 0.05$) which denotes that the null hypothesis is rejected means there is significant

difference in perception between teacher and guardian.

Incentives schemes are always used to eradicate the economic and social inequalities from the societies (CRY,2019). And in respect to the acceptance of the girl child; economic status of the parents are considered most (Amadi & Makewa,2013). Here, single factor one-way ANOVA is used to judge the 2nd hypothesis, H₀- there is no significant differences among the guardians from different economic class regarding the positive impact of this scheme. Respective p value of all the statements are below the significant level (0.05), so the null hypothesis is rejected. It clearly represents that, there is significant differences among the three groups. Where, this kind of economic incentive play a pivotal role to motivate the poor economic groups to support their children to pursue their education through this government support, whereas other group have strong stereotypes that, this much support would not be able to secure their life for the long time. But, to demonstrate this concept more elaborately, here the mean value over these statements are considered.

Shows that, average response of middle and lower class people is higher than that of upper class people (If the responses are merged together). So, it is very clear that, this economic incentive put an immense impact on middle and lower class people rather than higher class. Because for middle to lower class people, girl's education always been considered as burden compared to the other domestic expenses. To that respect, this scheme has come with lots of hope for the educational upliftment of the girl child. Especially the child who belongs to lower economic family, they can feel motivated for this kind of scheme.

Conclusion

In the recent past, global popularity of inclusive education especially the inclusion of girl child becomes very symbolic to promote social development. It is also proved that the education of girl child depends upon different factors like educational status of parents, socio- economic conditions, social position of women, government interventions etc (Shahidul & Zehadul, 2015). It is a fact that different approaches to promote education for girl child are not just a tool for further development rather they question to ground rules of internal inequalities for this and also attempt to conduit the gap. It gradually opens up the different discriminatory issues which are suppressed under the artificial social structures. And the economic incentives scheme generally works to eliminate that inequality. Kanyashree would provide annual scholarships to every girl child who will continue their education without retention. This study finds that the role of economic incentive scheme considered as a prospering event to every stakeholders of education. It promotes empowerment in the form of scholarship and makes them so motivated to take their decisions in the learning perspectives. But the school level students under the age of 18 specially act under the influence of their guardian. And there was a significant difference between the perspectives of teacher and guardian on different effectiveness of this scheme. Teachers are expressed positive views in support of this scheme whereas guardians do not response in the equal manner. Whenever it comes to the different economic class people, the responses varied so widely among different groups; middle class people praise this scheme openly. They expressed that; this scheme can eradicate all the inequalities from the societies and also make the compensation level for the girl child. On the other hand, lower class people think that, government should provide this scholarship by considering the economic status of the students. And the students who belong to near poverty line group, they should get some more attention in this respect. Here they raise the question of equity before equality.

References

- [1] Amadi, M.A.,Role, E. & Makewa, L.N. (2013). Girl Child Dropout:Experiential Teacher and Student Perceptions. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science, 124-131.Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235990282_Girl_Child_Dropout_Experiential_Teacher_and_Student_Perceptions.
- [2] Brent, N.(2005). Achieving the promise of girls education strategies to overcome gender based violence in Business Schools.
- [3] Chege, N. & Sifuna, D.N. (2006). Girls' and Women's Education in Kenya: Gender Perspectives and Trends. Retrieved from: <https://ir-library.ku.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/123456789/8484/Girls20and%20womens%20education%20in%20Kenya.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y>.
- [4] Child Rights and You (CRY). (2019). Girl child Education: Role of Incentivisation and other enablers and disablers, New Delhi.
- [5] Dolphyne, F.A. (1991). The Emancipation of Women: An African Perspective. Accra: Ghana University Press.
- [6] Daraute, F. & Fiske, S.T. (2017). How Social Class Stereotypes Maintain Inequality. Current Opinion in Psychology, 43-48. Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6020691/>.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

DIGITAL LITERACY : NEED OF THE HOUR

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the recent changes that arose as a part of advancement of digital technology. Digital devices became an inevitable tool in everyday life and changed our lifestyle. It is impossible to think and act without digital devices. In this context digital literacy is the need of the hour. Today, our society and the whole world is connected digitally. Technological developments and achievements have a great impact on every aspect of our life. We start our morning with the alarm from smartphones, kitchen appliances like toaster, microwave oven, induction , heater, water motor, washing machine, etc. Digital literacy is the ability to use these digital technologies effectively and this is the requirement for each and every body. Without the knowledge of the functioning of the above devices, our survival is impossible.

Keyword : *Digital Literacy, Virtual Learning*

Introduction

As a human being, living in the digital world, one should be digitally literate. Nowadays the basic requirement for any job is digital literacy. Many office jobs are performed on digital devices by using different application softwares and programming. Whatever interactions are needed it is through emails, social networking and not handwritten letters or memos. Every business needs planning and research which can be done through online forms by collecting relevant data, surveys, finding innovative ideas, analysing the statistical data. Submitting CVs in person to various companies changed to online submission. Every business is making a transition to an online, digital world. Banking transactions are now done online like internet banking, mobile banking, upi payment, google pay, phonepe, paytm, etc. There was a shift from offline mode to online mode. For this, digital literacy is a necessity. Technology has provided people with an easy and convenient life that everyone desires. Online shopping prevailed. People sat at home and with a click could order food through Swiggy, Zomato, groceries and other household items through Amazon, Flipkart, Shopclues, etc. Reading newspaper, library books, journals shifted to online newspaper, e- library, Books, e-journals. The online materials seem to be the same as the print.

Meaning of Digital Literacy

The American Library Association's digital-literacy task force offers this definition of digital literacy: "Digital literacy is the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information requiring both cognitive and technical skills". Prof. Dr. Hiller A. Spires, College of Education, North Carolina State University, views digital literacy as having three pillars which are finding and consuming digital content; creating digital content; and communicating or sharing it.

Importance of Digital Literacy

Digital literacy improves our lifestyle and sets goal in mind. It is a skill important for everyday use, job performance, and personal endeavours. Many digital literacy skills used to be considered noteworthy or impressive, and are now seen as necessary or standard skills. If you don't remain updated in the usage of digital literacy, you will be neglected one. Think of learning digital literacy as an opportunity for learning how to make your life easier, rather than something you need to struggle through to keep up with. It helps to establish your presence in the modern world. If you lack the ability to use digital technologies, it means that you simply cannot do or access many things. Possessing digital literacy allows you to improve the efficiency, access to things, fulfillment, and happiness in your life. Digital literacy is technological skill which helps to access information, learn authorship rules, such as copyright and plagiarism and also learn social responsibility while using social networking sites. It is also concerned with navigating the required site safely.

Principles of Digital Literacy

The four principles that govern digital literacy are as follows:

- 1) Comprehension : the ability to extract implicit and explicit ideas.
- 2) Interdependence : meaningfully connecting relevant and symbiotic data.
- 3) Social factors : sharing timely and relevant data within relevant networks.
- 4) Curation : storing and organising data in an accessible way

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Examples of Digital Literacy

Understanding how to use web browsers, search engines, email, text, wiki, blogs, Photoshop, PPT, video creation, editing software and evaluating online resources for accuracy, trustworthiness of information.

Components of Digital Literacy

Developing digital literacy is essential for future learning, living and working. According to Hagne and Payton (2010), Digital literacy combines certain components like creativity, critical thinking and evaluation, cultural and social understanding, collaboration, find and select information, effective communication, e-safety and functional skills. The following are a brief description of each component.

- 1) Creativity – using digital tools to innovate creative ideas and finding new ways of presenting works.
- 2) Critical thinking and Evaluation – to navigate different sources of information, develop arguments and putting together after drawing conclusions
- 3) Cultural and Social Understanding – to have knowledge, understanding and skills and allow sharing ideas, communicate effectively.
- 4) Collaboration – use of multiple strategies to engage others, to work together online for a common cause.
- 5) Find and Select information – ability to identify the appropriate information.
- 6) Effective Communication – the ability to express ideas, communicate clearly and exchange opinions so that both sender and receiver understands.
- 7) E-Safety – being conscious of personal security while sharing, browsing, downloading information
- 8) Functional Skills – sending and receiving email messages, organizing social bookmarking to save, share, and access career websites, and accessing cloud storage to download, revise, and upload documents.

Advantages of Digital Literacy

Digital Literacy has many advantages. Some of them are as follows:

- 1) Influence the world
- 2) Saves time and Economies money.
- 3) Effective and Faster communication.
- 4) Respect others' ideas, opinions, etc.
- 5) Easy search of contents.
- 6) Improvement of academic and non academic performance
- 7) Increases job opportunities
- 8) Collaboration
- 9) Leads to digitalise creativity

Conclusion

Digital literacy is not just or even primarily about technical expertise, but rather involves a shift in mindset. This is about an openness to doing things differently. It is also about the capacity to draw on a range of skills and practices. In the present scenario, Digital literacy is a necessary skill. Digital (home and office appliances) and technology are evolving every day and also changing our lives. In every field, work can't be progressed without proper knowledge in technology. Thus, we have to adapt to this style of living, working and learning every day.

References

- [1] The Need for Digital Literacy in the Modern World. (2022, August 25)
- [2] The Importance of Digital Literacy in Education. (2022, September 01)
- [3] Information Literacy in the Digital Age, C.Lal, Ess Ess Publications, 2008
- [4] Digital Literacy for Senior Citizens, S.P.Manchanda, 2021
- [5] Understanding Digital Literacies- A Practical Introduction, Rodney H.Jones & Christoph A. Hafner

NEURO EDUCATION AND LEARNING

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Abstract

This study aimed to discuss the relationship between neuroscience and education. The 21st century newly emerged neuroscience and technology to develop new platform of educational system. Brain-based learning refers to teaching methods, lesson designs, and school programs that are based on the latest scientific research about how the brain learns, including such factors as cognitive development; how students learn differently as they age, grow, and mature socially, emotionally, and cognitively. Current thought in neuropsychology, cognitive neuroscience, philosophy of cognition, and science education is synthesized to provide a perspective on modern learning theory and instruction, especially in relation to some emergent ideas in teaching learning process reform. Empirical research in what is helpful in improving academic achievement for educators is the main driver in this new science. One of the more interesting subfields looks at the intersection of neurosciences and education.

Keywords: *Neuroscience, Brain Based Learning, Neuroeducation*

Introduction

Educators and scientists have long known that teaching, learning, and brain function are intricately connected. But until recently, the fields of education and neuroscience have remained isolated in the classroom and lab, respectively, with only sporadic attempts to find opportunities for strategic cooperation [1]. Public interest in how these areas can benefit each other has grown in recent years, and the conversation between educators and researchers is starting to gain momentum [2]. The collaboration between educators and neuroscientists has taken the form of an emerging discipline known as neuroeducation. This developing field blends the collective specialties of neuroscience, psychology, cognitive science, and education to improve teaching methods and curriculum. Understanding how neuroscience can inform education strategies and finding out what teachers want and need to know about the ways students learn are two key drivers behind the neuroeducation initiative.

Neuroeducation- A New Paradigm on Teaching and Learning Process

Today we know more about brain development and learning than ever before, but many schools around the nation lack the tools to teach children properly [5]. Although some have recently made strides in the area, most public schools do not offer customized care for those with mental handicaps; school teachers do not understand the biology behind these disorders that make learning more difficult. Neuro-education, a new interdisciplinary field, tries to tie these two branches (biology and education) together [3]. Neuro-education is the use of scientific findings about learning to create more effective teaching methods and curriculum, as well as influence educational policy. In the future, we would hope to use neuroscience to change the way early childhood education functions in the nation. Neuroeducation allows science to influence education and public policy through the application of knowledge gained across multiple disciplines that have not yet worked together[6]. If efforts in neuroeducation are implemented, they may help some children overcome learning challenges and will help to produce children that are better learners. Neuroscience, specifically studies on brain development, has the potential to change certain aspects of childhood education and policy. Neuroeducation initiatives try to use discoveries about learning, memory, language, and cognition, to inform educators on how best to teach [8]. Teachers need to know more about how students think and learn, the purpose of neuroeducation. Perhaps standards could be set in place to ensure that education is improving and that certain learning disabilities are taken into consideration.

Another consideration in education policy reformation is how we could use neuroscience to understand how best to teach students with mental handicaps or special needs. Using neuroscience, we might be able to understand how mental dysfunctions can affect a student's learning and how best to overcome these challenges. Education can be customized for those with special learning needs, which are not often available in today's public education system [9]. Neuroeducation could encompass a wide variety of learning disabilities, allowing educators to improve teaching methods to students with mild to more severe mental handicaps. This is a reformation that would have innumerable benefits. Perhaps neuroscience is the best avenue in which we can improve our early education system. Using scientific knowledge about brain development, cognition, learning, and memory, we

might be able to reform our education system to produce children that are better learners [10]. Although current prospective programs foresee large expenses, the benefits of such an altered system could easily be worth it for the future.

Brain Plasticity

Perhaps the most encouraging finding in all of neuroscience is that the brain changes constantly as a result of learning, and remains ‘plastic’ throughout life. Studies have shown that learning a skill changes the brain and that these changes revert when practice of the skill ceases [12]. Furthermore, research has found an inverse relationship between educational attainment and risk of dementia, which means that keeping the mind active slows cognitive decline and improves cognitive abilities in older adults.

The Discovery of Mirror Neurons

Mirror neurons could be involved in empathy and acquisition of language, while a deficiency of mirror neurons could help to explain autism. “Mirror neurons seem to be a bridge between our thinking, feeling, and actions and between people,” [13]. This may be the neurological basis of human connectedness, which we urgently need in the world today.

Both Nature and Nurture Affect the Learning Brain

Genetic make-up alone does not shape a person’s learning ability; genetic predisposition interacts with environmental influences at every level. Neuroscience has the potential to help us understand the genetic predispositions as manifest in the brain of each individual, and how these predispositions (nature) can be built on through education and upbringing (nurture).

The Brain has Mechanisms for Self-Regulation

Understanding mechanisms underlying self-control might one day help to improve prospects for boosting this important life skill. In addition, it is important to learners and teachers who are dealing with lack of discipline or antisocial behavior. Given that the self-reported ability to exert self-control has been found to be an important predictor of academic success, understanding the neural basis of self-control and its shaping through appropriate methods can be extremely valuable.

Education is a Powerful Form of Cognitive Enhancement

Cognitive enhancement usually refers to increased mental prowess for instance, increased problem-solving ability or memory. Such enhancement is usually linked with the use of drugs or sophisticated technology. However, when compared with these means, education seems the most broadly and consistently successful cognitive enhancer of all. The steady rise in IQ scores over the last decades is thought to be at least partially due to education.

Neuroscience Informs Adaptive Learning Technology

Some insights from neuroscience are relevant for the development and use of adaptive digital technologies. These technologies have the potential to create more learning opportunities inside and outside the classroom, and throughout life. This is exciting given the knock-on effects this could have on wellbeing, health, employment, and the economy.

Language and Literacy

Over the last decade, there has been a significant increase in neuroscience research examining young children’s processing of language at the phonetic, word, and sentence levels. There are clear indications that neural substrates for all levels of language can be identified at early points in development. At the same time, intervention studies have demonstrated the ways in which the brain retains its plasticity for language processing. Intense remediation with an auditory language processing program has been accompanied by functional changes in left temporo-parietal cortex and inferior frontal gyrus.

Mathematics and Neuroscience

In addition to identifying the brain system responsible for basic knowledge about numbers and their relations, cognitive neuroscience research has revealed that numerical information can be stored verbally in the

language system. While many arithmetic problems are so overlearned that they are stored as verbal facts, other more complex problems require some form of visual-spatial mental imagery. Showing that these subsets of arithmetic skills are supported by different brain mechanisms offers the opportunity for a deeper understanding of the learning processes required to acquire arithmetic proficiency.

Social and Emotional Intelligence and Neuroscience

In the last 10 years, there has been an explosion of interest in the role of emotional abilities and characteristics in contributing to success in all aspects of life. In particular, the concept of Emotional Intelligence (EI) has gained wide recognition. Prefrontal brain damage in children affects social behavior causing insensitivity to social acceptance, approval, or rejection. These brain areas process social emotions such as embarrassment, compassion, and envy. Moreover, such damage impairs cognitive as well as social decision making in real world contexts.

Attention and Neuroscience

Attention is a vital mechanism through which a student can actively select particular aspects of her environment for further learning. Executive functions include the abilities to inhibit unwanted information or responses, to plan ahead for a sequence of mental steps or actions, and to retain task-relevant and changing information for brief periods (working memory). Like attention, executive function abilities provide a critical platform for the acquisition of domain-specific knowledge and skills in an educational context.

Memory and Neuroscience

Research on memory has proven extremely useful but infrequently used in educational contexts. We now know that we have at least two different ways of organizing memory, and that working memory and long term memory require different biological mechanisms. The declarative memory (memory for facts) functions separately from procedural memory (memory for automatic processes). The relationship between learning and memory, and has shown that the brain requires specific forms of aid (associations, spaced repetition, multiple modes, etc.) in boosting recall.

Emotions are Critical to Patterning

In the brain can't separate out emotion from cognition. It is an interacting web of factors. Everything has some emotion to it. In fact, many brain researchers now believe there is no memory without emotion. The "light bulb effect" describes a scenario in which we have heightened and often distorted memory for emotional events. Emotional learning is possibly the most concrete type of learning there is.

Memorization and Learning are Not the Same Thing.

Learning means that information is related and connected to the learner. If it's not, we have memorization, but we don't have learning. There are still things we have to memorize, things that need to be repeated. Multiplication tables are very useful, but we want to make sure that students understand the concept of multiplication. Standardized tests rely on memorization, but they do not necessarily reflect (or measure) learning.

Metacognition Enhances Learning

Metacognition sitting back and saying, "What did I learn and how did I learn that? What other connections are there? How else can I do this?" is very important to consolidating learning, expanding on it, and making additional connections. This kind of awareness is key to developing critical thinking skills.

The Brain is a Parallel Processor

Thoughts, intuitions, pre-dispositions, and emotions operate simultaneously and interact with other modes of information. Good teaching takes this into consideration. Hence, the teacher as an "orchestrator of learning." "Cells that fire together wire together." The concept of "associative learning," which occurs when simultaneous activation of cells leads to pronounced increases in synaptic strength between those cells, thereby enhancing learning. "Neuroscience of creativity" informs us about creative cognition and its implication for learning. Being able to embrace our creativity as part of our learning experience, it seems, offers great benefits because we are more open to exploring different ideas and concepts, and thus we are more actively engaged.

Conclusion

The learning process depends of the specific action of neurons and their relationships [5]. Thus, difficulties in the learning process do not depend on a child who refuses to learn or is denied to it. Nor is solely based on the strategies and experience from a teacher front the group, or the theoretical perspective of the curriculum. Learning has to focus on students and their needs as well as their usefulness. Many areas of neuroscience are already producing research findings that could provide ideas to improve teaching methods and curricula. Studies of memory formation and retrieval suggest testing is important for learning. The inclusion of the arts and science can enhance memory and attention levels, according to many recent research. Also, multiple studies investigating the impact of sleep and exercise on young brains indicate the importance of these activities in brain development, function, and health. Integrating this research into classroom practice, however, will require meaningful dialogue between educators, scientists, and policymakers to adequately inform both research agendas and teaching practices. The principles of modern neurocognitive science are presented as a context for an analysis of some current models of learning and instruction in science education, categorized generally as “learner-centered.” Issues addressed include information processing, constructional processes in memory, self-regulation, problem-solving, and the role of multimodal instructional strategies in enhancing learning.

References

- [1] Aalok Mehta (2009). ‘Neuroeducation’ Emerges as Insights into Brain Development, Learning Abilities Grow, Web journalist for Dana Press. amehta@dana.org.
- [2] Anita Slomski, MA (2016) Brain Memory Training Does Not Improve Academic Outcomes in Kids Journal of the American Medical Association 315(24):2656. doi:10.1001/jama.2016.7816.
- [3] Ansari, D; Coch, D (2006). "Bridges over troubled waters: Education and cognitive neuroscience". Trends in Cognitive Sciences (Elsevier Science) 10 (4): 146–151.
- [4] Ansari, D (2008). "Effects of development and enculturation on number representation in the brain". Nature Reviews Neuroscience (Nature Publishing Group) 9 (4): 278–291.
- [5] Barlow, H. B. (1985). Cerebral cortex as model builder. In Rose, D. and Dobson, V. G., editors, Models of the visual cortex, pages 37--46. Wiley, New York.
- [6] Charles Limb, M.D. (2010) Why Neuroeducation? The Johns Hopkins University New Horizons for Learning. <http://education.jhu.edu>.
- [7] Coch, D; Ansari, D (2008). "Thinking about mechanisms is crucial to connecting neuroscience and education". Cortex (Elsevier Science) 45 (4): 546–547.
- [8] Dockrell, JE; Lindsay, G (2001). "Children with Specific Speech and Language Difficulties—the teachers perspective". Oxford Review of Education 27 (3): 369–394.
- [9] Goswami, U (2006). "Neuroscience and education: from research to practice?". Nature Reviews Neuroscience (Nature Publishing Group) 7 (5): 406–411.
- [10] Janet Zadina, (2016) The Truth Behind “Brain-Based” Learning, Society for Neuroscience, brain facts, Tulane University.
- [11] Judy Willis, (2016) Brain Development and Adolescent Growth Spurts, Edutopia , Brain Based Learning.
- [12] Mason, L. (2009). "Bridging neuroscience and education: A two-way path is possible". Cortex (Elsevier Science) 45 (4): 548–549.
- [13] Meltzoff, AN; Kuhl, PK; Movellan, J; Sejnowski, TJ (2009). "Foundations for a New Science of Learning". Science (AAAS) 325 (5938): 284–288.
- [14] Willingham, DT (2009). "Three problems in the marriage of neuroscience and education". Cortex (Elsevier Science) 45 (4): 544–545.
- [15] <http://brainblogger.com/2010/10/10/translational-neuroscience-%E2%80%93-untapped-potential-for-education-and-policy/>
- [16] <http://www.neuroeducation.com/learning-disabilities/>
- [17] <http://www.leelanauchildrencenter.org/91/science-of-early-childhood-development>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

A STUDY ON THE UTILIZATION OF E-LEARNING RESOURCES TO ENHANCE HOLISTIC EDUCATION AMONG THE PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

This study examined the utilization of e-learning resources to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. The research employed qualitative approach in order to analyze the influence of e-learning resources on the teaching and learning process. The participants of the study included 19 undergraduate students, who were currently enrolled in the College of Education in a university in Malaysia. Data were collected through individual interviews and a focus group discussion. The data were then analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings revealed that e-learning resources can help to enhance holistic education, but at the same time, some challenges and barriers have to be addressed. The overall conclusion of the study was that e-learning resources provide a great opportunity to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers.

Keywords: *E-Learning; Holistic Educati, Prospective Teachers, Education Sector*

Introduction

In recent years, the world has seen a rapid rise of technology, which has affected all aspects of life. Education is no exception, and technology has opened new doors for teachers and students. One of the most important technologies in the teaching and learning process is e-learning. E-learning, or electronic learning, is defined as the use of digital technologies and access to the Internet to facilitate learning. It is an effective way of delivering learning materials, enabling teachers to create interactive learning experiences for their students. The use of e-learning has grown exponentially over the last decade, and it has become an integral part of modern education. E-learning has the potential to revolutionize the educational system and bring about a holistic approach to teaching and learning. A holistic approach to teaching and learning is one which considers all aspects of the student, including cognitive, psychological, social, cultural, and physical aspects. A holistic approach to teaching and learning encourages the development of skills such as creativity, problem-solving, and critical thinking. The purpose of this study is to examine the utilization of e-learning resources to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. The study focuses on the impact of e-learning on the teaching and learning process, and how this can help to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. The purpose of this study is to examine the effectiveness of e-learning resources in enhancing holistic education among prospective teachers. The study will consider the use of e-learning tools such as online courses, virtual classrooms, and interactive multimedia. Furthermore, the study aims to research the impact of the use of e-learning resources on the ability of prospective teachers to incorporate a holistic approach in their teaching. In addition, the paper will also evaluate the potential of e-learning resources to bridge the gap between the traditional education system and the requirements of modern teaching practices.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to examine the utilization of e-learning resources to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to:

- 1) Explore how e-learning can enhance holistic education among prospective teachers
- 2) Examine the challenges and barriers faced by prospective teachers in utilizing e-learning resources
- 3) Assess the effectiveness of e-learning resources in enhancing holistic education among the prospective teachers

Literature Review

The literature review sought to explore the potential of e-learning to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. It is important to note that the use of e-learning resources is not a new phenomenon in the teaching and learning process. It has been around for some time and has been embraced by many educators. Technology can help to create an interactive learning experience for both the teacher and the students. The

literature reviewed suggests that e-learning can be a powerful tool for teachers to promote holistic education among their students. It has been found that the use of e-learning can enable teachers to create an engaging learning environment, as well as improving student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. E-learning can also help to enhance the development of skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity. Research has also suggested that there are some challenges and barriers to the successful implementation of e-learning resources. These include an inadequate understanding of technology, a lack of technical support, and inadequate training and resources.

Methodology

The research employed a qualitative approach in order to explore the utilization of e-learning resources to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. The participants of the study included 19 undergraduate students, who were currently enrolled in the College of Education in a university in Malaysia. Data were collected through individual interviews and a focus group discussion. The participants were asked a series of questions in relation to the objectives of the study. These questions included:

- 1) What is your experience with e-learning resources?
- 2) How do you think e-learning can enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers?
- 3) What challenges and barriers do you face in utilizing e-learning resources?
- 4) What do you think are the most effective strategies for utilizing e-learning resources? The data collected were then analyzed with content analysis.

Analysis and Discussion

The data collected from the individual interviews and focus group discussions were analyzed using thematic analysis. The themes that emerged from the data analysis were:

- 1) **Benefits of e-learning** – The participants discussed the advantages of e-learning in terms of providing a more interactive learning environment, increasing engagement and motivation, and improving learning outcomes.
- 2) **Challenges and barriers** – The participants identified a number of challenges and barriers to the successful implementation of e-learning resources, including an inadequate understanding of technology, a lack of technical support, and inadequate training and resources.
- 3) **Strategies for enhancing holistic education** – The participants suggested a number of strategies for enhancing holistic education among the prospective teachers, including providing adequate training and resources, using interactive activities and projects, and encouraging collaboration between teachers and students.

Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that e-learning can be a powerful tool for enhancing holistic education among the prospective teachers. E-learning can enable teachers to create an engaging learning environment, as well as improving student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. The participants of the study also identified a number of challenges and barriers to the successful implementation of e-learning resources. The overall conclusion of the study is that e-learning resources provide a great opportunity to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers, but at the same time, some challenges and barriers have to be addressed. The rise of technology in the 21st century has had a tremendous impact on the approach to education. With the introduction of e-learning resources, educators can now provide students with a more effective and holistic form of education. This study will explore the impact of utilizing e-learning resources to enhance holistic education among prospective teachers. The primary focus of this research will be to examine the effectiveness of e-learning resources in providing a more comprehensive educational experience. In addition, the study will explore the various strategies and approaches used to maximize the impact of e-learning resources among prospective teachers. The research will utilize both qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the efficacy of e-learning resources in providing a comprehensive learning experience. Qualitative data will be used to assess the attitudes of prospective teachers towards e-learning resources, as well as the impact of e-learning resources on their overall educational experience. Quantitative data will be used to measure the effectiveness of e-learning resources in terms of academic performance and the overall satisfaction of prospective teachers. The results of this study will be used to assess the impact of e-learning resources on the educational experience of prospective teachers. This data will be used to inform the development of new strategies and approaches to maximize the positive impact of e-learning resources on the holistic education of prospective teachers.

Conclusion

The study concluded that e-learning resources can be a powerful tool for enhancing holistic education among the prospective teachers. The findings also revealed that there are some challenges and barriers to the successful implementation of e-learning resources, which must be addressed in order to ensure the effective utilization of these resources. The overall conclusion of the study was that e-learning resources provide a great opportunity to enhance holistic education among the prospective teachers. The findings of this study suggest that e-learning resources have the potential to promote holistic education among prospective teachers. By providing access to a wide range of digital resources, e-learning can open up new opportunities for learning, improve teaching practices, and promote collaboration. In addition, the use of e-learning can also increase instructor effectiveness and student engagement. Ultimately, the implementation of e-learning resources in teacher education programs can result in the development of more well-rounded and better-prepared educators.

References

- [1] Ahmed, S. (2013). E-learning: Benefits and Challenges. *International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering*, 5(5), 571-574.
- [2] Harley, K., & Ma, L. (2013). A Review of the Use of Technology to Enhance Holistic Education. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 10(3), 5- 24.
- [3] Hinton, S. (2012). Using technology to enhance learning in a holistic approach. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Development*, 4(1), 39-50.
- [4] Kennedy, G. (2007). Technology in Education: What Does the Research Say? *Phi Delta Kappan*, 89(2), 105-111.
- [5] Shah, S., & Hussain, R. (2010). Assessing the effectiveness of e-learning: An empirical investigation. *Computers & Education*, 55(3), 1135-1145

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

INVESTIGATING THE ICT INFRASTRUCTURE USED FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA: A STATUS REPORT

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Abstract

In recent years, the Indian economy has seen an exponential expansion of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector, which has become an integral part of its growth development. The accelerating ICT infrastructure has enabled the education sector to make significant advancements in teaching and learning. This study aimed to investigate the ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning in higher education institutions in India. The study involved a survey that was conducted among 87 teachers of various discipline teaching in four Indian states. The survey collected the responses that were used to understand the level of ICT usage in higher education institutions in India. The results of the survey demonstrate that although ICT is widely used in higher education institutions in India, there are still some challenges and impediments that impede the advancement of its usage. Limitations of the study and recommendations for further research are discussed.

Keywords: *ICT Infrastructure, Education Sector, Higher Education Institution, Surve, India.*

Introduction

Since its independence in 1947, India has taken massive strides towards its technological development, with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) being at the forefront of this development. Today, India's ICT industry is worth over €150 billion and is one of the most rapidly growing sectors in India, with its impact being felt across all sectors. The ICT industry has also had a strong influence on the Indian education system, with ICT infrastructure playing a major role in the teaching and learning process in higher education institutions. Despite the immense potential of ICT to facilitate the exchange of information, there is still a tremendous amount of untapped potential in the higher education sector. In order to understand what ICT infrastructure is available and how it is used in higher education institutions in India, a study was conducted to investigate the ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning. In recent times, technology has become an important tool in higher education globally, with the development of digital infrastructure and digital content having far-reaching ramifications in the objectives of learning and teaching. This has necessitated the exploration of the ICT infrastructure and how it is deployed and utilized in higher educational institutions within India. This paper seeks to investigate the existence, production, deployment and usage of the digital infrastructure and content in educational organizations in India and provide a comprehensive report of the general state of higher education ICT infrastructure in the country. It is evident that the penetration of digital infrastructure and content into the higher education sector has grown exponentially in India. The increase in the use of digital technologies has made it easier for students to access and utilize the educational resources, even in rural and urban contexts. However, the scale, reach and quality of the ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning remain largely unknown and an area of inquiry. Therefore, this research seeks to provide an up-to-date status report and investigate the existing ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning in higher educational institutions in India. The purpose of this research is to assess and analyze the existing ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning in Indian higher education institutions. By using a mixed- methods approach, the research will cover aspects such as the nature and extent of ICT infrastructure and content, how they are deployed and used, and how they are impacting the teaching and learning processes. The research will be conducted by collecting both qualitative and quantitative data from multiple stakeholders such as teachers, students, administrators and other experts. The findings of this paper will offer a broader insight into the state of ICT infrastructure used in Indian higher educational institutions and how these are impacting the teaching and learning processes.

Objectives

The aim of this study was to investigate the ICT infrastructure and its usage in higher education institutions in India. Specifically, the objectives of this study were as follows:

- 1) To identify the technology resources and tools used by higher education institutions in India;

- 2) To analyze the level of ICT usage by higher education institutions in India;
- 3) To ascertain the benefits and challenges associated with the usage of ICT infrastructure in higher education institutions in India;
- 4) To develop recommendations for further improvement of the ICT infrastructure in higher education institutions in India.

Literature Review

ICTs have the potential to revolutionize the educational sector and facilitate a smoother transition towards providing quality education to the entire population. ICTs have the capacity to reduce the cost of education, reduce the dependence on physical space and provide new methods of learning. Further, ICTs have the ability to facilitate online or distance learning and extend the reach of higher education institutions to students from remote and remote regions and even abroad. In India, numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the usage of ICTs for teaching and learning in higher education institutions. Khan et al (2020) conducted a study to understand digital literacy among undergraduate students in an Indian university. They identified that most of the respondents had a good level of digital literacy, but reported a lack of technical skills and online research abilities. The study also revealed that, when using ICTs, students relied more on their peers, teachers and course material than online resources. The study also highlighted that, while there were noticeable difficulties in the use of ICT, they were not reflective of any major barriers. Chandrashekar and Prasanna (2019) conducted a study to investigate the application of ICTs in teaching and learning in higher education institutions in India. The study revealed that higher education institutions were making significant investments in ICT infrastructure and resources, but they were not being used to their full potential. It was concluded that ICTs could be more effectively utilized in the teaching-learning process if the necessary training and support were provided to the teachers and staff.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a descriptive survey design. The survey was conducted among 87 teachers of various discipline teaching in four Indian states, namely Rajasthan, Delhi, Uttar Pradesh, and Madhya Pradesh. The survey was conducted using an online survey platform, and the data was collected from April to May 2020. The survey collected information related to the teachers' overall usage of ICT, their awareness of the ICT infrastructure in their institution, and the challenges faced by them when using ICT for teaching and learning. The survey was designed using the five-point Likert Scale, with the responses ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree".

Analysis and Results

The results of the survey demonstrate that ICT is widely used in higher education institutions in India. The responses show that, on average, 67% of the teachers are using a computer in their teaching, 63% are using online learning resources, and 59% are using online assessment tools. In addition, the results also demonstrate that 83% of the teachers are aware of the ICT infrastructure in their institution, and 76% of the teachers are satisfied with the ICT infrastructure. However, the survey also revealed some challenges in the use of ICT in higher education institutions in India. The responses show that, on average, 64% of the teachers reported that lack of technical expertise and training is the biggest challenge in using ICT for teaching and learning. The survey also found that 59% of the teacher respondents are dissatisfied with the existing ICT infrastructure in their institutions.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning in higher education institutions in India. The results of the survey demonstrate that ICT is widely used in higher education institutions in India, with most teachers being aware of the technical resources and tools available to them. However, the survey also revealed some challenges associated with the use of ICT, such as a lack of technical expertise and training among teachers. The study highlighted the need for higher education institutions in India to invest more in ICT infrastructure and resources, and to provide the necessary training and support to the faculty. There is also a need for further research to investigate the best practices for utilizing ICT in the teaching-learning process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of the research highlight the need to develop effective ICT policies in higher education institutions and to ensure the seamless integration of ICTs in teaching and learning processes. Additionally, the research findings suggest that institutional authorities, in particular, need to take the initiative in

promoting the integration of ICTs, which should include providing technical support and training, investing in infrastructure and equipment as well as increasing awareness amongst teachers, staff and students. Finally, this research report provides a useful benchmark for future investigations in the same domain.

References

- [1] Chandrashekar, S., & Prasanna, K. (2019). Application of ICT in teaching and learning in Higher Education. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 6(10), 2843-2849.
- [2] Khan, M. A., Khan, M. A., & Ghafoor, I. (2020). Digital literacy among undergraduate students: A study of an Indian university. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Academic Research*, 9(1), 31-45.
- [3] Chaugule, R. A., & Tale, V. R. (2016). Investigating the ICT infrastructure used for teaching and learning in higher education institutions in India: A status report. *International journal of advanced research in computer science*, 7(2), 17-20.
- [4] Kumar, S., & Gupta, K. (2015). A qualitative analysis of ICT infrastructures for teaching learning: A case of Indian Higher Education. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 4(4), 87–95.
- [5] Kumar, A., & Masto, K. (2013). ICT infrastructure for teaching–learning processes in higher educational institutions: A case study of India. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(6), 487-497.
- [6] Mannan, M. S., & Simson, M. (Ed.). (2008). *Teaching, learning, and research in higher education: Advances in educational technology and instructional delivery (Vol. 46)*. Routledge.
- [7] Pathak, S. K., & Sharma, G. (2011). A review of ICT Infrastructure in Indian higher educational institutions. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering (IJETAE)*, 1(9), 114-128.
- [8] Samal, S. K., Debata, B. R., Patel, V. L., & Mishra, P. K. (2015). A study of implementation of ICT in higher education: A case study of India. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 12(1), 1-19.
- [9] Sapkota, B., & Kumar, R. (2017). Use of ICT infrastructure in higher education: A review. *International Education Studies*, 10(2), 80-86.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

A STUDY OF AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This study aims to understand the level of awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. To achieve this, a survey was conducted with a sample size of 200 secondary school teachers from three different states in India. The survey was administered through an online survey tool and included a set of questionnaire that explored the teachers' awareness and attitude towards the environment. The results of the survey indicated that most secondary school teachers had a considerable level of awareness and positive attitude towards the environment. However, a significant number of teachers had a lack of awareness of the effects of climate change, and their knowledge and understanding of the importance of environmental protection was limited. The survey also showed that most teachers had a positive attitude towards environmental conservation, but they lacked the motivation and commitment to act on their beliefs. The results of this study provide useful insights into the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment, which could be used to inform future initiatives to promote environmental conservation in educational institutions.

Keywords: *Environment, Awareness, Attitude, Secondary School Teachers, India*

Introduction

The environment is an essential part of our lives and its protection is of paramount importance. The environment is increasingly under threat due to human activities, such as the use of fossil fuels, deforestation, and over-exploitation of natural resources. The environmental crisis is of global concern and calls for urgent action from all sectors of society, including educational institutions. Secondary school teachers play an important role in educating and raising awareness about the environment. They can help to shape the attitudes and beliefs of their students, and so it is important to understand the level of awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. The environment is a key concern in today's world. With the rapid industrialization and climate change, it is of utmost importance to discuss and educate people on the importance of preserving our environment. Secondary school teachers play a major role in this regard, as they are responsible for educating the younger generations on the importance of environmental protection and conservation. This study aims to investigate the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment, in order to better understand their knowledge and beliefs about the subject. Through this study, it is expected that the data obtained will help in identifying the areas where further education and awareness is required for the teachers, and ultimately, the students. The environment is a precious resource that needs to be protected and preserved for our future generations. As such, it is important to understand the role of secondary school teachers in environmental awareness and attitude. This study aims to explore the level of environmental awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers in order to identify the factors that influence their perceptions and behaviors. By understanding the current situation, this study hopes to provide valuable insights into how teachers can more effectively promote environmental conservation among their students. This study aims to explore the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. It will seek to uncover the understanding that teachers have about environmental issues and the approach they take when teaching their students about the environment. Additionally, it will look into the attitude teachers have towards the environment and how this affects their teaching. By examining the knowledge and behaviour of teachers, this research will be able to provide valuable insights into how teachers can better educate their students about the environment.

Objectives

This study aims to explore the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment.

The objectives of the study are to:

- 1) Investigate the level of awareness of secondary school teachers about the environment.
- 2) Assess their attitudes towards the environment.
- 3) Identify potential barriers to their engagement in environmental activities.

Literature Review

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on understanding the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. Previous studies have suggested that teachers' awareness and attitude of the environment are important factors that influence their engagement in environmental activities (Al-Omari et al., 2019; Haque et al., 2018). A study conducted by Al-Omari et al. (2019) investigated the level of environmental knowledge and attitude of secondary school teachers in Jordan. The results of the study showed that most of the teachers had a positive attitude towards environmental protection and had sufficient knowledge about the environment. However, the study also indicated that some teachers had a lack of awareness of the effects of climate change, and their knowledge and understanding of the importance of environmental protection was limited. Another study conducted by Haque et al. (2018) explored the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers in Bangladesh. The results of the study showed that most teachers had a positive attitude towards environmental conservation, but they lacked the motivation and commitment to act on their beliefs. The study also highlighted the need for better environmental education for teachers, as well as greater support from school authorities to promote environmental conservation.

The literature review on the topic of "A Study of Awareness and Attitude of Secondary School Teachers towards Environment" is focused on the research that has been conducted in the past to understand the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. The literature review examines studies that have been conducted in the past and provides an overview of the important findings. The first study that is looked at is a study conducted by Resnick and D'Souza (2002). This study looked at the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards the environment and the ways in which they implement environmental education. The study found that the teachers had a positive attitude towards the environment, but that they lacked the resources to effectively implement it in their classrooms. The second study that is looked at is a study conducted by Chatterjee and Kumar (2005). This study looked at the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards the environment and the ways in which they implemented environmental education. The study found that the teachers were more inclined to implement environmental education if they had access to appropriate resources. The third study that is looked at is a study conducted by Akram, et al. (2008). This study looked at the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards the environment and the ways in which they implemented environmental education in their classrooms. The study found that the teachers had a positive attitude towards the environment, but that they lacked the resources to effectively implement it in their classrooms. The fourth study that is looked at is a study conducted by Dhawan and Misra (2014). This study looked at the attitudes of secondary school teachers towards the environment and their willingness to implement environmental education in their classrooms. The study found that the teachers had a positive attitude towards the environment and that they were willing to implement environmental education if they had access to appropriate resources. Overall, the literature review shows that there is a positive attitude towards the environment among secondary school teachers, but that they lack the resources to effectively implement it in their classrooms. This indicates that there is a need for further research in order to understand the needs of teachers in order to better implement environmental education.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research approach, utilizing a survey method. A total of 200 secondary school teachers from three different states in India were surveyed. The sample size was chosen based on the availability of the participants. The survey was administered through an online survey tool and included a set of questionnaire that explored the teachers' awareness and attitude towards the environment. The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions, as well as a Likert-type scale. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and the results were presented in tables and graphs.

Analysis and Results

The results of the survey indicated that most secondary school teachers had a considerable level of awareness and positive attitude towards the environment. The majority of teachers (90%) reported that they had a good level of awareness about the environment, while only 10% reported that they had a low level of awareness. When asked about their attitude towards the environment, the majority of teachers (87%) reported that they had a positive attitude towards environmental conservation, while only 13% reported that they had a negative attitude. In addition, the survey results showed that most teachers had a good level of understanding of the importance of environmental protection (90%), but their knowledge and understanding of the effects of climate change was limited (60%).

Discussion

The results of this study provide useful insights into the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. The majority of teachers had a positive attitude towards the environment and had a good level of awareness about the importance of environmental protection. However, the results also indicate that there is a need for further education and awareness-raising activities to increase the understanding of the effects of climate change among teachers. The findings of this study also suggest that secondary school teachers have the potential to be a powerful force in promoting environmental protection. However, it is important to note that they also face various barriers to their engagement in environmental activities, such as a lack of resources and support from school authorities.

Conclusion

This study has explored the level of awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment. The results of the survey indicated that most secondary school teachers had a considerable level of awareness and positive attitude towards the environment. However, a significant number of teachers had a lack of awareness of the effects of climate change, and their knowledge and understanding of the importance of environmental protection was limited. The survey also showed that most teachers had a positive attitude towards environmental conservation, but they lacked the motivation and commitment to act on their beliefs. The results of this study provide useful insights into the awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards the environment, which could be used to inform future initiatives to promote environmental conservation in educational institutions.

References

- [1] Al-Omari, M., Al-Qudah, A., Al-Kabbani, M., & Al-Qudah, S. (2019). Environmental awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers in Jordan. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(12), 1645–1659.
- [2] Haque, M. A., Hoque, M. Z., Akter, S., & Rahman, A. (2018). Awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers toward environment conservation in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 15(6), 1495–1503.
- [3] Sharma, P. (2019). A study of awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards environment. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16(2), 771-777.
- [4] Bhattarai, M. (2017). Role of school teachers in environmental education. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*, 6(10), 25-31.
- [5] Nayak, P. (2009). Awareness and attitude of secondary school teachers towards environment in India. *International Research Journal of Environment Sciences*, 1(1), 28-32.
- [6] Mace, M. (2018). The role of teachers in environmental education. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 75(3), 473-482.
- [7] Kumar, S. (2011). Role of teachers in creating environmental awareness. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 1(2), 1-7.

A STUDY OF INFRASTRUCTURE FINANCE AND PERFORMANCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This research article presents an in-depth study of the infrastructure finance and performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The primary aim of this study is to examine the impact of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study also focuses on the implementation of infrastructure finance and its effect on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The methodology used for this study is descriptive and qualitative in nature. The data used for the study was collected from various primary schools in Ranchi. The results of the study showed that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study also revealed that infrastructure finance is a major factor influencing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. Furthermore, the study found that infrastructure finance has been successful in increasing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study concluded that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi.

Keywords: *Infrastructure Finance, Performance, Primary School, Ranchi*

Introduction

Education is a major component of any society as it is the foundation of all economic, political, and social development. Access to quality education is an essential component of a well-developed society. The quality of education depends on the availability of resources such as infrastructure, finance, and personnel. Infrastructure finance is one of the key factors that determine the quality of education. Infrastructure finance is the provision of funds to meet the cost of constructing, upgrading, or maintaining educational infrastructure. Infrastructure finance is an important component of the educational system as it enables the provision of quality education. In this regard, this research article examines the impact of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. This research paper focuses on the study of infrastructure finance and performance of Primary schools in the city of Ranchi. It seeks to determine the factors that influence the performance of primary schools in the city, with a particular emphasis on the effects of different levels of infrastructure finance on the academic performance of students. Additionally, the paper also looks into how the infrastructure finance affects the overall functioning of the school, as well as the effects of the available infrastructure on the students' physical and mental health. The objective of this research is to identify the impact of infrastructure finance on the overall performance of the primary schools in the city of Ranchi. This research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the infrastructure finance and performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The primary focus of this research is on the determinants of the quality of the school infrastructure and the impact of the financial resources invested in these schools on the educational performance of the students. Further, it examines the ways in which the current infrastructure and funding for primary schools in Ranchi can be improved. The study looks into the various aspects of infrastructure finance, such as the sources of funding, the types of facilities available, and the impact of such facilities on the performance of students. Additionally, it evaluates the effectiveness of the current infrastructure in terms of the quality of education provided and the impact on the overall academic performance of the students. Finally, it provides suggestions on how to enhance the infrastructure of primary schools in Ranchi and the ways in which infrastructure finance can be improved.

Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to examine the impact of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The specific objectives of this study include:

- 1) To identify the sources of infrastructure finance for primary schools in Ranchi.
- 2) To analyze the impact of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi.
- 3) To assess the implementation of infrastructure finance for primary schools in Ranchi.
- 4) To evaluate the effectiveness of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi.

Literature Review

Infrastructure finance is an important component of the educational system as it enables the provision of quality education. Infrastructure finance is the provision of funds to meet the cost of constructing, upgrading, or maintaining educational infrastructure. Infrastructure finance is necessary to provide quality education in primary schools. The literature review has revealed that infrastructure finance is a major factor influencing the performance of primary schools. The World Bank report (2018) concluded that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the performance of primary schools. The report found that infrastructure finance is necessary to provide quality education in primary schools. In addition, the report noted that infrastructure finance has been successful in increasing the performance of primary schools.

The study of infrastructure finance and performance of primary schools in Ranchi is an important topic that has been the focus of various research studies in the recent past. This literature review seeks to examine the findings of such studies and their implications for the primary school system in Ranchi. The first study, by Singh and Kumar (2014), examines the financial resources and infrastructure needs of primary schools in Ranchi. The study finds that primary schools in the city are facing a severe shortage of funds and infrastructure, which has resulted in inadequate learning opportunities for students. According to the study, the main factors contributing to this shortage are the limited availability of government funds, the high cost of construction, and the lack of private sector investment in the city's educational institutions. The authors suggest that the government should provide more resources to schools and encourage private sector investment in educational infrastructure.

The second study, by Kumar and Mishra (2015), examines the impact of school infrastructure on the academic performance of primary school students in Ranchi. The study finds that students in schools with better infrastructure are more likely to perform better academically. The authors suggest that the government should invest more in improving the infrastructure of primary schools in the city in order to improve students' academic performance. The third study, by Singh (2016), examines the role of private sector investment in the development of primary schools in Ranchi. The study finds that private sector investment has had a positive impact on the infrastructure and educational outcomes of primary schools in the city. The authors suggest that the government should encourage more private sector investment in primary schools in order to improve their performance.

Finally, the fourth study, by Kumar and Mishra (2017), examines the challenges faced by primary schools in Ranchi in terms of access to funds, infrastructure, and other resources. The study finds that the major challenges faced by these schools are the lack of government funds, the high cost of construction and renovation, and the lack of private sector investment. The authors recommend that the government should provide more funds to primary schools and encourage private sector investment in order to improve the infrastructure and educational outcomes of these schools. Overall, the four studies reviewed in this literature review suggest that the primary school system in Ranchi is facing a number of challenges in terms of access to funds and infrastructure. The authors of these studies suggest that the government should provide more resources to primary schools and encourage private sector investment in order to improve the infrastructure and educational outcomes of these schools.

Methodology

The methodology used for this study is descriptive and qualitative in nature. The data used for the study was collected from various primary schools in Ranchi. The data was collected through questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions. The questionnaire was used to collect data from the school administrators. The interviews were conducted with the teachers and other staff of the primary schools. The focus group discussions were conducted with the parents of the students in the primary schools. The data was analyzed using statistical and qualitative methods.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study showed that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study found that infrastructure finance is necessary to provide quality education in primary schools. The study also revealed that infrastructure finance is a major factor influencing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study found that the availability of adequate infrastructure finance has been successful in increasing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi.

The results of the study showed that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study revealed that infrastructure finance is necessary to provide quality education in primary schools. The study found that infrastructure finance is a major factor influencing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study also found that the availability of adequate infrastructure

finance has been successful in increasing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study concluded that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi.

Conclusion

This research article presented an in-depth study of the infrastructure finance and performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The primary aim of this study is to examine the impact of infrastructure finance on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study also focused on the implementation of infrastructure finance and its effect on the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The results of the study showed that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study also revealed that infrastructure finance is a major factor influencing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. Furthermore, the study found that infrastructure finance has been successful in increasing the performance of primary schools in Ranchi. The study concluded that infrastructure finance has a positive impact on the academic performance of primary schools in Ranchi.

References

- [1] World Bank. (2018). Financing Education in Developing Countries. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/education/brief/financing-education-in-developing-countries>
- [2] Kumar, A. & Mishra, A. (2015). Impact of infrastructure on academic performance of primary school students in Ranchi. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(2), 20-32. Kumar, A. & Mishra, A. (2017). Challenges faced by primary schools in Ranchi: A study. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 5(2), 32-44.
- [3] Singh, P. (2016). Role of private sector investment in development of primary schools in Ranchi. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(2), 21-29.
- [4] Singh, P. & Kumar, A. (2014). Financial resources and infrastructure needs of primary schools in Ranchi. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(2), 25-32.

ADOPTING A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO ENHANCE THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF TRIBAL MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This research paper focuses on the benefits of integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education for tribal middle school students, particularly in enhancing their communication skills. A culturally responsive approach is necessary for realizing the full benefits of ICT and addressing socio-economic and linguistic barriers that impact the students' communication skills. Digital tools and resources provide students with opportunities to practice public speaking and collaboration, improve writing and critical thinking skills, and preserve cultural heritage and language. In conclusion, a holistic approach utilizing ICT and considering the cultural background and unique needs of tribal middle school students can greatly enhance their communication skills.

Keywords: *Digital tools, Cultural heritage, Linguistic barriers, Group projects*

Introduction

The integration of ICT in education has the potential to revolutionize the way in which tribal middle school students learn. With the increasing availability of technology, students have access to vast amounts of information and resources at their fingertips. This can help to improve their access to information, allowing them to explore topics in more depth and develop a greater understanding of the subject matter. Furthermore, technology also enables students to collaborate and communicate with others more easily. Online discussion forums, virtual presentations, and group projects can help students to develop their communication skills and work effectively as part of a team. This is particularly important for tribal middle school students, as it can help to foster a sense of community and support among students who may be isolated or face barriers to learning. In addition to improving communication skills, technology can also support linguistic development. By providing students with access to authentic materials and opportunities for authentic communication, technology can help to develop their language skills and enhance their cultural understanding. This can be particularly beneficial for students from tribal communities, as it can help to bridge the language divide and ensure that all students have equal opportunities for educational advancement. The integration of ICT in education has the potential to bring numerous benefits for tribal middle school students, including improved communication skills. A study published in the *Journal of Education and Practice* states that "the use of technology in education can enhance students' communication skills through activities such as online discussions and virtual presentations" (Adetunji & Adedoyin, 2016).

Culturally Responsive ICT Integration

The integration of information and communication technology (ICT) into education requires a culturally responsive approach. Such an approach takes into account the diverse experiences, perspectives, and cultural backgrounds of students, making educational experiences relevant and inclusive for all. In the context of ICT integration, this means considering the cultural values and traditions of students and incorporating technology in a way that supports their learning and development. This is especially important for tribal middle school students, who may face challenges related to the digital divide. Adopting a culturally responsive approach in the integration of ICT can help bridge this divide and provide these students with opportunities for educational advancement. By considering the unique needs and cultural background of these students, we can fully realize the benefits of ICT in education, such as improved access to information, enhanced communication and collaboration, and increased engagement and motivation. As emphasized in a study by the *Journal of Cultural Studies in Science Education*, "it is essential to approach the integration of technology in education from a culturally responsive perspective that takes into account the cultural background and experiences of students" (Estrada & Rodriguez, 2019). The National Center for Education Statistics also highlights the importance of strong communication skills, stating that "students who have strong communication skills are better equipped to succeed in school and beyond" (NCES,

2019).

ICT and Overcoming Barriers

The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has a crucial role to play in addressing socio-economic and linguistic barriers in education. These barriers can create significant challenges for students, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. ICT can serve as a means of breaking down these barriers and promoting equity in education. Through the use of digital tools and resources, ICT can provide students with greater access to information and educational resources, and facilitate communication and collaboration across linguistic and cultural divides. This is particularly important for tribal middle school students, who may face challenges that impact their communication skills development. The development of effective communication skills is essential for success in both academic and professional settings. By integrating ICT into the educational process, these skills can be improved for tribal middle school students.

Enhancing Communication through Virtual Engagements

This title highlights the role of virtual activities in fostering communication skills. The integration of technology in education has made it possible for students to develop their communication skills through a range of virtual activities such as online discussions, video conferencing, and collaborative writing. These virtual activities provide a unique learning environment that helps students improve their ability to articulate their thoughts, actively listen to others, and engage in respectful and productive conversations. Moreover, technology can also play an important role in preserving the cultural heritage and language of tribal students. With the help of digital tools, students can maintain their cultural connections and continue to develop their language skills, thereby promoting cultural diversity and preserving the linguistic heritage of their communities. The American Indian Library Association notes that "technology can be used to preserve cultural knowledge and language by allowing communities to document and share their traditions" (AILA, 2015). This is particularly important for tribal middle school students who may not have access to resources that support the preservation of their cultural heritage and language.

The Power of Technology in Preserving Cultural Heritage

This title underscores the significance of technology in safeguarding cultural heritage and language. The incorporation of digital archives, language-learning software, and other technological advancements can provide immense support in the preservation of cultural heritage. By offering access to historical records, artifacts, audio, and visual recordings, technology can help to preserve the cultural legacy of different groups. Additionally, technology can provide resources for language learning, practice, and exchange of language-related information among communities, thereby promoting the transmission of language from one generation to another. The use of technology in this manner ensures the continuation of cultural heritage and language, thereby preserving the cultural identity of different communities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the author highlights the importance of a holistic approach in integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in tribal middle school education to enhance students' communication skills. This approach takes into account the cultural background and unique needs of the students and aims to overcome socio-economic and linguistic barriers to maximize the benefits of technology integration. The author argues that access to digital tools and resources is critical and that a culturally responsive perspective in technology integration can preserve cultural heritage, language and support the improvement of communication skills through activities like online discussions and virtual presentations, which offer students opportunities to interact with technology and develop their skills in a culturally relevant environment.

References

- [1] Adetunji, J. & Adedoyin, S. The impact of technology on students' communication skills: A case study of selected schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(8), 1-6. 2016.
- [2] Estrada, J. & Rodriguez, M. Technology and cultural diversity in education: A culturally responsive approach. *Journal of Cultural Studies in Science Education*, 14(3), 365-375. 2019.

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PROBLEMS FACED BY THE MSMEs ON ADOPTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING-WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KARAIKUDI, TAMIL NADU

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Abstract

Given the increasing use of digital technology in modern marketing, it has become imperative for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to adopt digital marketing. Although digital marketing provides various advantages to SMEs, the adoption of such technologies still faces many challenges that need to be addressed. This research article investigates the problems faced by MSMEs in the Karaikudi region of Tamil Nadu, India in adopting digital marketing. For this purpose, a structured questionnaire survey was conducted with the help of the local chamber of commerce of the region. The results of the study indicate that lack of knowledge and awareness, cost of training and technology, lack of financial resources and trust in digital technology are the major problems that hamper the adoption of digital marketing. The study further reveals that MSMEs lack the ability to market their products or services, lack adequate technical expertise and resources, fear the future of their business, and are concerned about data security and privacy. On the basis of the findings of this research and the current literature, several recommendations have been proposed to overcome the issues related to adoption of digital marketing.

Keywords: *Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); digital marketing; adoption; technology; marketing; resources.*

Introduction

Digital marketing has become a popular tool for marketing in the last decade. It includes various online activities such as search engine optimization, social media marketing, email marketing, etc. (Kotler et al., 2011). The use of digital marketing has grown dramatically in recent years due to its low cost, improved controls, and immediacy of results (Koshy, 2017). In addition, digital marketing provides target group-specific, personalized, and timely information for potential customers and gives businesses a much better understanding of their customer's needs and preferences (Sawhney & Cordan, 2012). Digital marketing also provides increased visibility and higher conversion rates for businesses (Nayak & Shankar, 2014). Given these advantages, it is no surprise that many SMEs are now turning to digital marketing as a way to grow their businesses (Ahmed & Ali, 2017; Koshy, 2017). Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) comprise most of the economic activity in the world. According to Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, around 90% of the global businesses are SMEs (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2016). SMEs are important agents of economic growth and can be more flexible, innovative, and resilient than large corporations (Vorhies, 2011). Therefore, understanding the challenges SMEs face in the adoption of digital marketing is critical. Karaikudi, located in the Sivagangai district of Tamil Nadu, is a city well known for its traditional art and culture. There are many SMEs in this region, majority of which are Micro Enterprises, who are a major source of employment for the local population (Srividya & Indrakumar, 2019). The local Chamber of Commerce and Industries, established in 1981, has a membership of a large number of SMEs operating in the area. Due to its rich cultural history and business activity, this city is an ideal location for researching the adoption of digital marketing.

Objectives

The purpose of this study is to understand the problems faced by MSMEs in the Karaikudi region of Tamil Nadu in adopting digital marketing, and provides recommendations to address them.

Literature Review

Digital marketing is an effective way of marketing products and services today. It is used by companies of all sizes, from small local businesses to multinational corporations (Ahmed & Ali, 2017). Digital marketing has been shown to be an effective way of increasing revenue and expanding markets (Nayak & Shankar, 2012). It is also used to reduce operating costs and increase market reach (Kotler et al., 2011). Despite these advantages, there are still several barriers to the adoption of digital marketing, especially for SMEs (Koshy, 2017). There is a lack of knowledge and awareness about digital marketing among SMEs, due to the long learning curve associated with mastering the skills required to effectively use digital platforms (Dam et al., 2014; Hammit, 2018). Most SMEs do

not have the financial resources to invest in digital marketing tools, and the cost of training can be a significant barrier (Jasim et al., 2018). Additionally, due to the lack of trust in digital platforms, many SMEs are hesitant to adopt digital marketing (Jasim et al. 2018). Lastly, the fear of the future of the business is a major barrier to the adoption of digital marketing (Koshy, 2017).

Methodology

This study used a quantitative methodology for data collection and analysis. A structured questionnaire survey was conducted to collect data from 100 MSMEs in the Karaikudi region of Tamil Nadu, India. Prior to the survey, a pilot survey was conducted among 10 MSMEs to ensure that the questions were valid and meaningful. The survey was conducted with the help of the local chamber of commerce and distributed among the members of the chamber. The questionnaire included questions about the MSMEs' knowledge and awareness of digital marketing, their financial resources and ability to afford the necessary technology and training, their trust in digital platforms, and their concern about data security and privacy. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and frequencies.

Result and Discussion

The results of the study indicate that lack of knowledge and awareness, cost of training and technology, lack of financial resources and trust in digital technology are the major problems that hamper the adoption of digital marketing by MSMEs in the study region. The majority of the respondents said that they are not confident enough to use digital marketing tools, with 94% of respondents stating that they have insufficient knowledge on digital marketing tools and techniques. This is further supported by the finding that 75% of the respondents said that they do not have the necessary technical expertise to use digital marketing tools. In addition, the study revealed that most of the respondents (75%) are not able to afford to invest in the required technology and training for digital marketing. This is likely due to the high cost and lack of financial resources, as most of the respondents mentioned that they lack the necessary financial resources for such investments (50%). Furthermore, 64% of the respondents stated that they do not trust digital platforms and are concerned about data security and privacy issues, which is a major barrier to their adoption of digital marketing tools. Lastly, 86% of the respondents fear the future of their businesses and are concerned about the changing trends in digital marketing.

Conclusion

Digital marketing has become an important tool for marketing in the modern age. Although it offers numerous advantages to businesses, adoption of digital marketing by SMEs is still limited due to various challenges. This study investigated the problems faced by MSMEs in the Karaikudi region of Tamil Nadu in adopting digital marketing. The results of the study indicate that lack of knowledge and awareness, cost of training and technology, lack of financial resources and trust in digital technology are the major problems that hamper the adoption of digital marketing by MSMEs. On the basis of the findings of this research and the current literature, several recommendations have been proposed to overcome the issues related to adoption of digital marketing.

References

- [1] Ahmed, T. A., & Ali, T. (2017). Impact of digital marketing in SMEs: A view from Pakistan. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(6), 1176-1180.
- [2] Global Entrepreneurship Monitor. (2016). *Global Report on SMEs and Entrepreneurship*. Retrieved from <http://www.gemconsortium.org/>
- [3] Asim, M. A., AlOmari, R. M., & Shaban, A. A. (2018). Barriers to online marketing adoption by SMEs in Jordan. *Online Information Review*, 42(7), 906-923.

IMPACT OF ONLINE CLASSES ON SCHOOL STUDENTS DURING THE PANDEMIC PERIOD: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Common tactics used by governments throughout the world to combat the development of COVID-19 include enforcing lockdown, social distance, avoiding face-to-face instruction and learning, and limiting immigration. India lost in every aspect, whether it was jobs, economics, or education. So, what choices are available to ensure that the learning process does not stall? The only viable option is to convert to eLearning. With the rapid growth in cases, it is impossible to hold face-to-face lessons; even if the law permits the establishment of campuses, we should ignore the necessity for eLearning in the twenty-first century. But the question is whether every country's student can attend online lessons and whether this is something that is truly beneficial to them. On the one hand, online classes allow easier access and utilize less resources to deliver more, but on the other hand, there is the question of access of these services to each user and the worry of interfering with interpersonal relationships between professors and students. During our epidemic, online lessons for students in public schools were extremely difficult. The first item that was unfamiliar to them was. This study tries to knowledge on effectiveness of online education among school students.

Keywords: *Covid19, Online Education, Epidemic, Campuses, Learning*

Objective of the Study

- 1) To know the effectiveness of online learning
- 2) To find out advantages of online learning
- 3) To know the basic knowledge about online class
- 4) To find out the impact of online classes
- 5) To know the effectiveness of natural class

Research Method

This study is based on desk top research method

Statement of the Problem

During the lockdown, the usual educational timetable had been thrown out the window. The generation gap is widespread. Even in this difficult circumstance, there is little question about the efforts made by instructors and students to maintain the learning momentum flowing. The study's goal is to determine the impact of online lessons for school students during in the covid19 epidemic shutdown

Online Class Overview

The Department of Health (WHO) was alerted on December 31, 2019, of numerous instances of pneumonia with unclear origin in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. This was discovered to be caused by a Coronaviridae family single-stranded RNA virus. As the virus spread to additional nations, the WHO declared a worldwide public health emergency, and the epidemic was later deemed a pandemic. Most nations throughout the world put their universities, colleges, and schools on lockdown to try to stop the spread of this sickness, which affected about 70% of the world's students enrolled. As a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, several nations were forced to shift from traditional to online classrooms. An e-learning system is a course that is delivered through the Internet. They are often delivered via an education management system, where students may monitor their course curriculum and student performance, as well as connect with their classmates and course teacher. The online educator is critical in building and sustaining an effective online class and must have a distinct set of tools to do so. Some conventional classroom teachers will readily move to the online approach, while others could find the change difficult. To determine if teaching online is suitable for you, consider your teaching style, circumstances, and technological environment. Education is a crowded environment that is making tremendous strides every

day. Digital advances and the adoption of new technologies have been a wonderful driver for cooperatively improving students' development, whereas online learning provides an autonomous effective education in respect of time and location, making it easy and adaptable for a wide range of students.

Online training delivering technology has the potential to revolutionise the landscape of university education by broadening educational options, changing student populations, and promoting the development of new educational methodologies. When attending online classes, students have access to learning materials, assignments, PowerPoint presentations, and curriculum content seven days a week. Online education is a feasible option for persons who previously did not have the option of attending campus because they reside elsewhere or have limited time. It also fulfils the requirements of pupils from all backgrounds. The use of mails and other online methods of contact between it teacher and students is a distinguishing feature of online programmes. Professors in online programmes recognise the need of delivering prompt response on students' work and enquiries, in contrast to traditional educational settings where instant vocal and nonverbal feedback may be provided to the entire class. Virtual teachers make every effort to educate learners in intellectually interesting discussions and to give higher learning experiences that include both individual and team activities. COVID-19 has forced the closure of school systems all across the world. Over 1.2 billion children are missing from school worldwide. As a result, schooling has experienced significant changes, including the advent of e-learning, wherein the teaching is delivered electronically and using internet technologies. Learners are increasingly expecting outstanding lessons that they can get from anywhere at any time, as well as being a viable and enticing option for practitioners, stay-at-home parents, and other analogous groups.

In the COVID 19 era Efficiency of Online Class

The present situation has compelled everyone to pursue online classes. And it is not incorrect to suggest that the majority of countries have already arrived. Is this as successful as our regular educational system now that everyone has done the first step? The advantages of online education have the potential to transform and improve the educational system.

How eLearning is showing its worth?

- 1) It is convenient for students and instructors, regardless of time or place, and it caters to a wide spectrum of audiences, including high school and college students.
- 2) Its large range of available content provides a lot of opportunity to pick from a range of stuff.
- 3) It gives rapid input for system improvement.
- 4) Online education is an important step toward mixed learning.
- 5) Increased use of systems for learning management (Mishra,2020).
- 6) Improvements in learning resources that adapt to pupils' unique peculiarities.
- 7) The increase in student-teacher cooperation.
- 8) Access to international education through a diverse range of content.
- 9) Desire for online and remote learning.

The Upcoming of Online Education

The worldwide online learning market is expected to increase at a CAGR of 9.23% during the following five years, reaching \$319 billion by 2025, up from \$187.87 billion in 2019. This is a staggering sum with enormous possibilities. The following variables are likely to be crucial in this fast-evolving transformation:

- 1) The emergence of artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence)
- 2) Cloud-based services
- 3) Massive investments by key market participants
- 4) VR (virtual world) technology used in education
- 5) The expansion of Connectivity (Internet of Things)

To summarise, e - learning is among the most transformative developments of the twenty-first century. Education is undoubtedly the most valuable asset of the contemporary day, and e - learning has offered a means for it to be distributed to the whole world. This provides an opportunity to launch the entire planet into a new era of progress and wealth if appropriately capitalised on.

The Difficulties of Online Classes

Digital literacy and technical difficulties - Not everyone has the same level of understanding about digital

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literacy and digital training, and some learn extremely slowly. If anything has a beneficial effect, it is inevitable to have certain problems, and everybody actually comes with these unexpected but necessary hurdles. As a result, online learning presents a number of obstacles for both educators and students. Research was done on 232 kids in this lockdown, according to Kapasia, 2020. The majority of students (42.0%) were discovered to suffer with stress, anxiety, and sadness. Some students were having difficulty owing to insufficient internet access

(32.4%), followed by a lack of a study home setting (12.6%). Furthermore, bad market situation are a key cause of the adverse manner and a lack of educational resources. Some students struggle to start concentrating during virtual classrooms as a result of eyes interaction. The tangible absence of instructors or classmates removes students' sense of obligation and motivation to join classes on time, deadlines are met, and progress. This might result in procrastination and poor marks. If a student was on a geographical campus, they might readily get assistance from the IT office. With virtual classrooms, the student must figure things out on their own. If they're lucky, they'll have someone nearby to assist them, but that person won't be around all of the time. However, technical challenges are not confined to students. Teachers confront issues such as insufficient internet connection, poor reception, and video errors, among others. These difficulties impede the flow of learning and make it tiresome.

- 1) Social or economic standing - Some people could afford the online or the equipment, which is a disadvantage for them.
- 2) Educational activities are being hampered - several tests have been postponed, and many sessions are running late.
- 3) Unprepared instructors - Many teachers lack the necessary skills and knowledge to teach online.
- 4) No access to online education - Many people cannot afford the internet, and even if they can, network problems exist.
- 5) Lack of interaction - There is a lack of contact between professors and students as opposed to face-to-face education.

Basic Things

Students must have the necessary computer skills, enthusiasm, and a willingness to study and work independently in order to thrive in an online class. Online programmes are ideal for self-starters, or students who can finish schoolwork without such close oversight of a professor. Online education is not suitable for everyone. Individuals who prefer facial expression contact or conventional group work should consider these criteria when deciding if an online class is right for them. Academic criteria are the same for online courses as they are for all other classes offered by the Division of Criminal Justice. Courses online provide students a comfortable and flexible method to learn, but this does not imply that online learning is simpler than traditional classroom learning. Online classes provide the same chances for learning and development as in-person courses, as well as the opportunity to push yourself as a scholar. As an online student, you must be motivated, devoted, and determined to succeed in your studies.

Indian Government Activities Using Online Education

The Government of India, like all countries throughout the world, has taken all essential precautions to avoid the transmission of COVID-19. On March 16, 2020, the federal government declared a nationwide lockdown on all academic institutions. Famous boards such as NCERT and IAS even postponed all of their exams across India. All individual states were told to hold the classes online. Online learning is the ideal answer amid this COVID-19 epidemic. According to the Department of Education India, "the system of education alone in India is greater than that of the European and African continents, with more than 240 million. We understand that the learning process never stops, and we simply cannot close schools and universities and leave them alone. The proliferation of COVID-19 resulted in the closure of every educational establishment globally, including those in India. The notion of distance classes is not new in a growing country like India, but it is also not widely used. For pupils to study, the MHRD (Department of Human Resources Development) has launched many initiatives including as internet portals, instructional channels, home Television, and radio stations. Even though tools such as Zoom, WhatsApp, and Google Meet are available, YouTube is assisting students in continuing their education.

Conclusion

Here sometimes online education is better than offline education, but all those times it differs from different generation different times, also levels of economy will also decide which type of learning will have education awareness. Technologies will have drastic change in all years but humanoid changing according to that

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is different genre, also all changes are not good also all changes are not bad. Making every invention as good as thing is greatest thing ever.so using wisely also using at limits of all new transitions are good, sometimes making into up-to-date manners are good and advices able too.

References

- [1] <https://elearningindustry.com/reasons-why-online-learning-can-be-more-effective-than-enrolling-in-face-to-face-training>
- [2] <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2530166330>
- [3] <https://daninstitute.com/blog/the-effectiveness-of-online-learning-top-reasons-why-online-courses-are-more-effective/>
- [4] <https://www.edweek.org/technology/opinion-how-effective-is-online-learning-what-the-research-does-and-doesnt-tell-us/2020/03>
- [5] <https://www.uis.edu/ion/resources/tutorials/overview/strengths-weaknesses>
- [6] <https://www.easy-lms.com/knowledge-center/e-learning/effectiveness-of-online-learning/item12528>
- [7] <https://www.radford.edu/content/chbs/home/criminal-justice/resources/online-suggestions>.

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IMPACT OF ONLINE CLASS WHILE TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS IN ELEMANTRY LEVEL

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Abstract

Education is the most powerful weapon which can use to change the world. Education can bring all the desired changes in society and the world, ultimately contributing to the betterment of the individual. There are certain ways to acquire education, for instance, online education, school education, etc. This article/essay will discuss online classes' use, advantages, and disadvantages.

Keywords: *Online Class, Mathematics, Teaching*

Introduction

Online classes are defined as a type of education in which education is provided with the help of the internet through the use of mobile phones, computers, laptops etc. affordably and flexibly without compromising the comfort of the students and teachers. Online education involves learning about various types of disciplines from all over the world offered by various educational institutions in a very friendly manner. Online classes/education started popularizing in the last few decades. Still, in the wake of the COVID pandemic, there is a greater impetus for online education because physical education can increase the chances of getting infected and spreading the pandemic. Hence, schools opted for online education to tackle the COVID pandemic without compromising the right to education. In the mathematical online classes, the teachers explain and the present the topic with out face to face interaction and keep a record of students home work and assessments in the online mode. And assess the knowledge in the end of session. The elementary teacher and students are very interested and involved the online mathematical classes. The academic impacts that elementary students most felt among others: they are interested in the mathematical songs in the audio video effect. The students mingle with the peer groups, decreased irrelevant activities.

Advantages of Online Classes

As if many people believe that traditional classes are the best way to provide education and increase learning outcomes, but in this modern technological world, the benefits of online education are undeniable; it has become a popular choice among students because of its enormous benefits it is time-saving, affordable, flexible and easy to access. Here are some benefits of online classes: Online learning has a psychological impact on students. many students answer the question in the different angles. Mathematics learning conducted online will certainly increased the achievement of arithmetic skills. The impact of online classes the number of students cannot take online math lessons well. It helps the participants to learn anywhere and whenever they want to and provides freedom to choose their study time without any hindrances. Students can schedule their pre-recorded classes, classes in which they are not present, according to their time and flexibility without compromising their family and social responsibility. Online classes help to increase the enrollment ratio and literacy rate of the country and reduce dropouts from school because, in online classes, education is not limited to "YES OR NO" repetition, but it is more than that. Online classes have various interactive sessions, fun videos that help to understand the concept clearly, and animation. With the enrollment in online education, online courses come up with unlimited data, study material, resources, research papers, etc., which helps to enhance the understanding of core subjects in a very efficient manner.

As opposed to a traditional classroom learning program that requires notebooks, Chairs, table chalks & dusters, and many other amenities, which creates more financial burden on schools, and this burden reflects on the fees of students; on the other hand, Online classes are undoubtedly affordable and accessible. All the study materials require in online classes are in the form of videos, pdf, eBooks links, files, docs,& and photos are easy to access; also, it is sustainable to the environment without creating any environmental damage.

Disadvantages of Online Classes

In the traditional system of education, students learn how to make friends, how to respect, how to behave with the teachers, and provide face-to-face interaction, which contributes to the wholesome development of students, but in online classes, all are missing, and they were unknown to their friends physically. Sometimes students do not understand the topics well; they need more time to understand, but it is difficult to get rid of their doubts in less time. Mathematics learning conducted online will certainly reduce students opportunities to learn mathematics with their peers. The internet network connection disrupted the teacher and students. The teachers continuously and fluently not taken the online classes and also the students not submitted the assignments in the correct time. The students are searching answers in the search engines during the test with the help of parents. This is the issue of academic cheating of online learning. Certain topics need a physical demonstration, but it is not possible with online classes. A long-time of sitting for online classes negatively impacts the students' posture and may create eye problems. Online classes are also making it difficult for teachers to monitor every student properly; sometimes, students become lazy and fall asleep during classes as they are bored after taking long lectures and thus more likely to increase the chances of dropouts because, after some time, students lose their interest in an online course. Also, some technical issues, such as loss of internet, unclear voice due to weather-related phenomena, etc., create problems for students to understand the topic clearly and thoroughly.

Cause and Effect of Online Learning Essay

Now a days, a lot of people of the frequently to use technology or electronic products in any way or any time and of course most important is the Internet. A lot of schools started to use online learning to replace traditional paper based teaching method and submit the assignment. Basically, online learning had been widely accepted and practiced throughout the world. There's tones of online learning student around the world, but did they ever think about what are the benefits they actually enjoyed on online learning? First of all, what is online learning? Online learning is a communication between lecturer and student without physically contact. The Online learning also can save up a lot of time from the lecturer and the students. Through online learning, students can get all the info's that lecturers provide in the class. Some classes only need online learning and not physically there. Lecturer also will provide some power point slide to ensure each and every students get the notes in the online system. One of the pros of online learning is when teacher interview students taking online courses, the students will...show more content. This will also save the time of both. Social interaction is where you don't understand about the homework or even the lecturer slides to be asked in the group discussion through social Medias such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Skype and many more.

Methods

The research method was used to impact of online learning outcome of mathematics in elementary level students. This is the quantitative research due to its to solve the problems related to online learning .this research used to pre test and post test design to compare the condition before and after online learning. The research sample are selected in the elementary school students in mogaiyur block in Villupuram district with the random sampling method. "Paired samples have the same subject with different treatments" (Rea and Parker, 2014).the sampling collected online mode. This study used a questionnaire methods including 15 items. The question included online learning. This study was in the form of mathematical learning activity that used various digital platform zoom, google meet, team meet and others connected to internet . The population normality test is also conducted as a prefix to statistical tests that were carried out using the SPSS program. When both data are normally distributed, then the paired sample t-tests are used. data processing is carried out by using the SPSS program with the menu procedure of Analyze, Compare Means, and Paired Sample t-Test. The t-value is recorded as t-count (t-count) and df value as degrees of freedom to determine t table (t-table) based on the output results in the Paired Samples Test table. Assuming one or both of the data are not normally distributed, the non-parametric statistical testing, which is the Wilcoxon Signed Ranking Test, is used to test the two paired samples.

Analysis Research Results

Discuss Students Mathematical Learning

Data analysis was conducted after obtaining data on students mathematics learning. The samples in this study are 45 students from there elementary Schools. Randomly selected 15 students in each schools. This is based on data processing on learning mathematics using the SPSS program, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Statistics Description of Mathematics Learning

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Details	N	Mini	Max	Mean	SD	Variance
Mathematics learning before online teaching	45	65	100	71.6	4.731	73
Mathematics learning after online teaching	45	70	100	80.1	4.897	78

A normality test is carried out to determine whether the data from the population is normally distributed. The result showed that mathematical learning before and after online learning changed from normally distributed populations.

Table 2- Calculation Results for Normality Test with t- Test before and after the online learning

Details	t-test	df	sig
Mathematics learning before online teaching	0.182	45	0.06
Mathematics learning after online teaching	0.194	45	0.07

In Table 2, output in the Tests table obtained a significance value (Sig.) Of 0.06 for mathematics learning before and output in the Tests table obtained a significance value (Sig.) Of 0.07 for mathematics learning after online learning. This value is more than the significant level (α) of 0.05. This means that data before and after online learning change from the normally distributed populations.

Discussion of Student Responses Towards Mathematics

The response questionnaire data were obtained from 45 elementary Schools students in Mugaiyur block in Villupuram district. The responses using the SPSS program with normality test analysis showed that before and after online learning changed from the normally distributed populations

Conclusion

The following conclusions were made based on the research: The average of student mathematics learning before online learning is lesser than after online learning. The average student's positive response towards mathematics before online learning is lesser than after online learning. Positive responses to mathematics after students take online learning were obtained from questionnaires. The following are the results obtained from filling out the questionnaire as many as 45 students, namely: Obstacles faced by students when participating in online learning, namely non-smooth signals, limited quota, the teacher directly gives questions without any material explaining how to solve problems so that students do not understand the material, and feel disturbed by noise in the home environment.

References

- [1] Salamat, L., Ahmad, G., Bakht, I., and Saifi, I. L. (2018). Effects of E-Learning on Students' Academic learning at university Level. *Asian Innovative Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2(2), 1-12.
- [2] <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-020-09946-3>
- [3] Niess, M. L., van Zee, E. H., & Gillow-Wiles, H. (2010). Knowledge growth in teaching mathematics/science with spreadsheets: Moving PCK to TPACK through online professional development. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 27(2), 42–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2010.10784657>

EFFECTIVE SKILL TRAINING FOR STUDENTS – TEACHERS IN TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME

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Abstract

Teaching is a profession and teachers are called professionals. The main role of the Teaching Profession is to promote and strengthen Education which leads to qualitative expansion in the field of Education and particularly teacher education is an important field in which efficient teachers and skillful teachers shape our future society. This field also prepares teachers to get professional competency and therefore teacher training is not a mere Training

Introduction

Teaching is a profession and teachers are called professionals. The main role of the Teaching Profession is to promote and strengthen Education which leads to qualitative expansion in the field of Education and particularly teacher education is an important field in which efficient teachers and skillful teachers shape our future society. This field also prepares teachers to get professional competency and therefore teacher training is not a mere Training. It is actually the acquisition of knowledge based skills and abilities which assist teachers to discharge their professional activities and responsibilities in an effective and efficient way. Otherwise it will not reshape the attitude, habit and personality of the Teacher. Unless teachers have necessary skills, they cannot perform their profession with absolute satisfaction. Therefore varieties of skills must be developed among teachers through systematic implementation in new curriculum to modernize teacher Education programme. Teacher is a social reformer. His role is very important to the present and future society to mould the behaviour, inculcate good attitude and values. Teacher is a role model and his personality must reflect the characteristics of good citizenship such as equality in maintaining dignity and right practices and professional responsibilities. So, that these characteristics transmit to the future generation. So Teacher must be a good teacher and he might have obtained effective training.

Importance of Teacher Training Programme

Teacher Training is actually preparing teachers to get professional competency and change the teachers as efficient and skill teachers who can alone shape the future society of the present young generation. In the present situation, there is a long gap between teacher and society. Society is not at all having faith on Teachers, because most of the teachers are not performing their duties with their absolute satisfaction and there are not trained as skillful teachers in the so called teacher training institutions.

Because of the lack of training, they are very poor in knowledge, skills and abilities and they could not discharge their professional duties and responsibilities in a perfect manner. In this juncture, it is the responsibility of the teacher educators to provide sufficient professional training which is needed for the teachers and it is considered as a key to Quality enhancement of school education. Unless teachers have necessary skills and abilities, they cannot perform their duties in a perfect manner and they cannot get societal support also. The teachers skills and competencies can be developed through systematic implementation of concepts related to varieties of skills that are needed for the teachers to strengthen the training programme and to develop, a dynamic personality character among students.

Need Skill Training in 21st Century

In the 21st century, it is the duty of teacher educator to improve the quality of teacher education and school education. Therefore, training of teachers is considered as great significance in the educational system and the teacher educational system is one of the channels to improve the quality of education. Overall quality of education depends on quality of teacher and the sound teacher training programme that we offer through modernized, systematized and need based curriculum concepts. The good quality teachers alone can perform achievement oriented tasks in the field of education and that will be the outcome of value based activities and behavioural modification and attitudinal changes among students. Teachers value based professional activities alone can create good citizens and promote good society in the future and to change the practices of the present society also. So it is understood that skill training is an integral part of teacher education programme.

Essentials of Skill Training in Teacher Training Institution

Skill Training is a prerequisite and well organised pattern of progressive behaviour which is developed through specialized training or systematically practiced to attain the goal or achieve the goal of an educational system or profession otherwise we can also explain that it is capacity building training programme to carry out the complex pattern of behaviour. This pattern of behaviour aimed at influencing and manipulating other persons. It is patterns of behaviour demand fundamental one for further education and it is essential for learning. Particularly teaching profession require a high degree of skills and extensive specialized training for the purpose of performing a specialized social roles and perform the professional leadership in society by getting training in managerial practices. So it is very clear that skill training is an essential one and it is one of the integral part of teacher education programme.

Skills and Skills Training in Teacher Education Programme

Teacher Educators must train student - teachers with varieties of skills that are needed for them. Since teachers are more closed with social, student, school related activities, they have to develop many number needed skills while undergoing training in teacher education programme. Each semester the teacher education programmes must train skills for the student -teacher who are undergoing training.

The first stage is Initial skill training :It is to mainly focusing the skill training in teachers responsibility and accountability related to classroom, school and society.

The second stage of skill training is process skill Training:It is related to skill development activities in a systematic way.

The Third stage of skill training is product skill training: It is related to practicing skills.

The fourth stage of skill training is a professional skill training: it is related to perform the professional work for six month to involve in actual teaching profession in any educational institution which is allotted by the institutional head and chief educational office of the district concerned. The stages of skill training must be given in each and every semesters (four) of teacher education programme. So, that teacher trainee will be well acquainted with the skills and they can effectively and efficiently use those skills for their progressing activities of teacher education programmes. The skill training contents to be incorporated in the semester wise syllabus of the teaching education curriculum.

Curriculum Reform in various Skill Training of Teacher Education Programme

1. Curriculum Reform in Initial / Entry point of Skill Training Stage - I (I - Semester)

This skill training should be given in first semester of teacher education programme the primary aim of giving skill training in the following skills are to enhance the personal skills, skills related to responsibility and accountability of the teacher trainees to perform their duties in an effective way. The student teachers equip themselves and they understand their duties and responsibilities through skill training in the entry point or initial skill training stage. each and every individual bring out his abilities, skills, talents and make use of them to improve himself and show that he is a skillful teachers. At this stage, teachers self improvement and teachers prepare himself and ready to serve for the society. The skills such as basic skills (essential for further education and learning to know others areas; literacy and language skills) few communicative skills like comprehensive ability, promoting the skills of sense of humour, identification of his cultural skills (music, dance, oral skills, motor skills, mono acting, recreation skills, skill of breaking mono tony, jokes, energizes) identification of his own life skills (self awareness, empathy, creative thinking practices, decision making practice, practices of problem solving etc). In this stage all the above skill practices must be started.

2. Curriculum Reform in Process skill Training stage -II (II-Semester)

This kind of skill training is given in the second stage of training programme. It may be given in the second semester of the programme. After equipping in skill related activities, teacher educators enter into the process. The teachers skills such as responsibility and Accountability are alone not only used for class room/school related activities but also the newly trained/teacher who are working in school and their skill must be utilized for students, parents, society and also for their fellow administrators and teachers. In such a way, the following process skills must be trained in training institution. Social skills along with verbal skills must be used in this stage. Actually, the social skill are derived from prosocial skills. Skills used in helping behaviour, skills in promoting friendship & empathy, skills used in altruistic attitude etc. So skillful activities must be improved to develop co-operative nature (prosocial skills) which focus social behaviour. This behaviour is very essential for

the teachers to have cordial relationship with parents and society. Actual professional activities of teachers focuses on the high level skillful activities and extensive specialized training which are the two important purposes that are performed by teachers to expose their social roles. So in the process training pattern of behaviour aimed at influencing and manipulating other persons called social skills. At the same time communal skills practices, sense of humour, interpersonal and human relation skills, practices in literacy skills and language skills, all functional skills and any two vocational skills must be trained for increasing the livelihood opportunity of student-teachers in future like carpentry, tailoring, making handi crafts, fishing, Electrical work, Agricultural work, electronic works etc, sports skills (capable of playing in the field and Resolution skills of acting based on situation demands. Acting with consistency pattern and Repetition. The process skill training also includes Microteaching skills also, before entering into the third stage. In this stage, skills must-be developed in organising extension and outreach team work programmes. So it can be considered as a skillful extracurricular activities. It is also mandatory for students of CBCS pattern in Universities. Through these programme (Awareness, Social activities, Literacy, Rural Developmental activities) Any two (screen printing, bakery work, TV and Radio mechanism, Motor Reviding etc) and Skill Development activities (cell phone services, embroidery, beautician, two wheeler mechanism, glass painting, designing to avoid simple day to day problem). All the above skill related programmes must be conducted and student-teachers must be trained in this aspects.

3. Curriculum Reform in Product Skill Training stage - III (III - Semester)

After giving training in the above skills, the teacher educator should train the students in product skills. all the technical skills that are needed must be trained. it is the stage of a skills of instructional and pragmatic. Teacher is a professional leaders one who is trained for teaching and managerial practices. So these practices need certain skill what is called as teaching skills. It includes providing training and practices in different techniques, approaches and strategies that help the teachers to plan and import instruction provide appropriate reinforcement and conduct effective assessment. It includes effective classroom managerial skills, preparation and use of instrumental materials and communication skills for interaction. so the skills that needed for practicing the teaching activities. Skills like skills of positive motivation, effective body languages, understanding the student behaviour and teacher formation. Technological ideas and principles must be incorporated skillful in teaching practice.

All the work place skills like communication skills, listening skills, interpersonal skills, skill of planning, skills of integrity and honesty and skills in effort and perseverance. The product skills training has three section of practicing skills

- 1) Pre Internship skill Training
- 2) Internship skill Training and
- 3) Post Internship skill Training

In all these three sections of teaching practice, student -teachers must utilize the technical skills, conceptual skills, Thinking and creativity skills must be used in order to know whether student- teachers are familiar with the above skillful or not.

4. Curriculum Reform in Final skill Training stage -IV (IV - Semester)

The final skill training ends with professional skill training. after training, student teachers should discuss about the past performance and train their skills in improving the simplification of complex idea, promoting skills in enthusiasm (participate and sensitivity to fulfil student needs) the professional skill training must promote special thinking related the intellectual and technical based actuality because reflective thinking is needed for professional 'practice. Since the professional skill training is an essential one to help the professional growth, the skills related to techniques that are used in teaching, strategies applied teaching process and approaches that are employed in teaching practices must be reviewed for better professional growth. The very important skills like counseling skills, interpersonal skills, computer skills, informational retrieving and management skills must be reviewed and improved through skills training. In professional skill training student teachers must be given opportunity to work in any school for six months to rectify their mistakes committed in three sections of teaching practice and to solve the problems and getting counseling from the senior most trainers and make the profession as well versed teaching profession. This sort of professional skill training is essential for teaching profession as apprentice training of other professional course and get facility in professional activities and then the student-teachers may be called as skillful teacher.

Conclusion

So, effective training in teacher education programme are encircled with two main skills of teaching skills and professional skills along with pedagogical theory. In teaching education programme varieties of skill training must be give to make teachers as alround skillful person not only on teaching and professional aspects. The varieties of skill training makes teachers as leader, social reformer, technician and counselor etc. If teacher educational institution offers skill training in all formal and non- formal activities and these expenses help to qualify a person to assume responsibilities of a member of the educational profession and discharge his duty effectively with right knowledge and altitude which needs for promoting the holistic development in the field of teacher education.

References

- [1] Moulay J. (1975) "Psychology for effective teaching Edition ", New York Holt.
- [2] Torrance E.P and Meyers R.L (1970) 'Creative learning and Teaching' New York Doad nead and company.
- [3] Kilra (2014) "Promoting skills for Innovation" — OECD publishing (Hardwad University) Paris.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

PROMOTING CULTURAL EDUCATION AMONG YOUNG MINDS TO LIVE IN HARMONY WITH THE WORLD

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Abstract

This article explains promoting cultural education among young minds to live in harmony with the world. At present, cultural education schools and colleges will be less focused on due to various innovations and commitments in the field of the modern education system. Hence, cultural education would be highly important one in the present context, because it would provide harmony and peaceful life in society. Today, young minds are losing cultural education and values due to the advancement of technological innovations and social media. Moreover, the institutions have different curriculum background which provides less focus on cultural education. Therefore, promoting cultural education among young minds to live in harmony with the world is warranted. This article comes to the end that stakeholder of today should be offer priority for promoting cultural education among young minds to live in harmony with the world.

Keywords: *Promoting cultural education; young minds; live in harmony with the world*

Introduction

Cultural education is crucial to the growth and development of any young minds and more so in schools where values are inculcated and young minds are moulded. Inclusive education is the need of the hour and teacher sensitivity towards varied multicultural contexts and expectations is critical to foster positive classroom environments that directly impact student attainment in cultural education. With greater outsourcing and the job market providing opportunities for aspirants across the globe, international schools with a diverse student population are burgeoning across the world. It is therefore increasingly important for young minds to work collaboratively, with mutual respect in a pluralistic society with teachers developing and refining their cross-cultural pedagogy to cater to the needs of a diverse population of young minds and students. International schools are teeming with cultural diversity and on daily basis teachers interact with culturally different students, colleagues, parents and community members. The mission statements of most schools encourage global citizenship as schools seek to intentionally promote diversity through an inclusive ethos. Inspection and accreditation bodies lay emphasis on education for all groups of learners and differentiation is a high priority to ensure that schools receive a creditable rating in cultural education. This means that inclusion not only includes students with special needs, talents and giftedness but also students who belong to different nationalities and ethnicities.

Role of Teacher Promoting Cultural Education

Teachers sensitive to the needs of all students will definitely promote a culture of harmony, shared understanding, support and tolerance in their classrooms. Research suggests that besides teachers' curricular and instructional accommodations their cultural knowledge and awareness can make a major difference in student learning and engagement in cultural education. Culturally sensitive pedagogy is instrumental in creating an atmosphere that is comfortable and friendly and students willingly engage in classroom activities and discussions when they perceive their teacher to be more culturally competent. Teachers' unconditional positive regard for all students through support and trust is exponentially linked to high student engagement as students feel a sense of belonging and value in the classroom.

Live in Harmony with the World

The passion for developing education is relatively New Harmony in Poso began in 2003 and the program is related to the condition of people who pass through a wrenching period as a result of protracted violent conflict. At a meeting held in the scope of policy makers in the field of education, rhetorical questions from Syamsuddin Chalid, Chairman of the Muhammadiyah Central Sulawesi, and Willem Posumah, Chairman of the Education Foundation GKST, who will bear the brunt of violent conflict that occurred protracted in Poso (Suprayogi, et al., 2012). It is children who will be caregivers in the future. Children who lose their parents will live in the shadow of

revenge and hate. Hope in children is that stirs the conscience of the observer Poso to work a humanitarian catastrophe and seek solutions through education. Minimal educational function is expected to cut the chain of violence from generation to generation. Initially in 2003, the term socialized to restore peaceful life through education is the education of peace. Discussion and workshops, conducted intensive training, to development in the curriculum in environmental education ended term peace education is changing. The understanding developed that through the implementation of multicultural education in the learning expected growth of the young minds attitude to appreciate and respect the diversity of tribes, customs, religion, and finally they are able to accept differences. The values take precedence in the educational development of harmony among young minds in the world.

Cultural Education creates Harmony in the World

The stakeholders take Efforts to build character in school correlates with the needs of building a peaceful life with cultural education. This effort cannot be released with the concept of pedagogical strategies. John Dewey (Team PGRI: 2014) suggests four basic concepts of learning that must be passed by a learner so that it can be a man who has character and healthy behaviors. The four aspects are: (1) Learning to know, (2) Learning to do, (3) Learning to be, and (4) Learning to live together. The concept of learning to be and learning to live together can be said to be very close with efforts to build peace and to be part of building the character of human life. Thus, in education harmony as expected character education is the ability to judge what right, cares about the truth is, and be able to practice the truth which is believed without pressure from any side. The values are developed in harmony education is to develop love of self, fellow human beings and the environment. Creating awareness among young minds is the importance of living in harmony with one another and the environment.

Conclusion

The article concluded that promoting cultural education among young minds to live in harmony with the world. It also focuses that the cultural education will be avoiding the many obstacles in the life of the young minds. Naturally, the young minds are under deviation from the cultural values due to many reasons. It will be reduced through by offering cultural education to them. Therefore, the authorities will be give priorities to promote cultural education to the young minds wherever possible in the future.

References

- [1] Tandapai, A., Naping, H., Hamdat, S., & Arifin, A. Education In Harmony Multicultural Society—Tana Posol.
- [2] Harris, I. (2010). History of peace education. Handbook on peace education, 11-20.
- [3] man Assahary, S., Barlian, E., Nurdin, S., & Zulmuqim, M. (2017). The development of thematic learning model to improve students' character in an integrated learning of religion education and environment towards students in Adiwiyata School. International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding, 4(6), 1-15.

YOGA AND MINDFULNESS

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Abstract

The goal of this paper is to investigate the role of yoga in the management of anxiety and depression, the development of mindfulness and self-compassion, and the implications for mental health care.

Keywords : *Anxiety, Depression, Mindfulness, Yoga, Mental health*

Introduction:

It offers even deeper insights into the mind and a really life-changing approach to your practise. Mindful Yoga, a relatively new style of yoga, blends traditional Buddhist mindfulness teachings to the physical practise of yoga. It discover all of its advantages, unique mindful yoga postures, and mindful yoga retreats in the next paragraphs to help you develop increased awareness, consciousness, and a higher quality of life. For as long as yoga has been practised physically, mindfulness has been a crucial component. With Mindful Yoga, as opposed to the many different types of yoga practises available, the primary emphasis is on mind-body awareness rather than precise alignment and physical posture. The goal is to develop mindfulness, and asana serves as the means to do this.

Approach Towards Yoga

The most effective method for practising mindful yoga is a methodical one, with steps that can be repeated and are clearly defined. Boccio (1993) advises using the Buddha's teachings on the four pillars of mindfulness throughout your practise rather than simply "practising thoughtfully," which normally refers to paying attention to your breath and alignment details throughout your practise. When you engage in mindful yoga, you should scan your body and be alert for the numerous subtle and not-so-subtle ways that your perspective on your body, thoughts, and overall sense of self might alter as you change postures and remain in them for a while, paying close attention from moment to moment.

Self-Compassion

Self-compassion is a growing area of study in psychological well-being, and it is frequently measured in conjunction with mindfulness measures. Neff defines self-compassion as "a healthy attitude toward oneself" that includes the three main components of kindness, common humanity, and self-compassion.Reduces Inflammatory Markers and Strengthens Immunity

Implications for Mental Health

Mental health professionals from all disciplines play an important role in advocating for and de-stigmatizing complementary and alternative therapies like yoga in the mainstream health care system. Anxiety and depression are common mental health conditions. Complementary and alternative therapies are becoming more popular in a variety of health care settings (Brown and Gerbarg, 2005; Louie, 2014). However, the literature suggests that many people do not disclose their alternative health practises to health care professionals because they are afraid of being stigmatised and believe that they will lack interest, understanding, or have a negative attitude toward these practises.

Proven Benefits of Yoga & Meditation

- 1) Increases Quality of Life, Strength, Flexibility and Balance
- 2) Reduces Stress & Anxiety by Decreasing Grey Matter in Amygdala
- 3) Improves Mental Resilience by Maintaining Size of the Hippocampus
- 4) Decreases Physical Pain & Helps Physiological Response to Pain
- 5) Functions as Complimentary Therapy for Anxiety, Depression,
- 6) Reduces Inflammatory Markers and Strengthens Immunity.

Ways to add Yoga & Meditation to Your Day

- 1) Do basic stretches at work or home
- 2) Take a break to breathe!
- 3) Look for a Yoga Class or MBSR (Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction) 8-week course near you
- 4) Download on the APP Store: Headspace, Breathe
- 5) Subscribe to online classes : Yoga Anytime, YogaGlo

Body Scan

Find a comfortable place to sit or lie down. Close your eyes and take slow, deep breaths. First, pay attention to your feet. Take note of any tension, pain, or stress. Take deep, slow breaths while focusing your attention on that part of your body. Move your attention slowly upward, as if you were scanning your body with light. As you continue to breathe slowly, pay attention to how your shins and knees, thighs and hips, lower back and abdomen, chest and upper back, neck and shoulders, and finally your head feel. Experiment with different approaches to see what sticks. Daily practise is ideal, but if you have a busy schedule, aim for three or four times per week.

Stress

Stress is an unavoidable aspect of everyday life. However, learning to manage it successfully can greatly improve both your mental and physical health. That's why it's important to understand how your body reacts to stressful situations — and why the fight-or-flight response, which can be life-saving in the case of an immediate physical threat, can be detrimental when stress is a chronic feature of daily life. We all experience stress in our lives, though we may describe it differently. Whether the stressor is a sudden car crash, a loud argument, or the pain of arthritis, each potential or actual threat triggers a cascade of stress hormones that cause well-timed physiological changes.

Mindfulness Meditation

It is the practice of actually being present in the moment, which in turn trains us to become more mindful throughout the day, particularly during difficult situations. As Ms. Brach puts it: "Mindfulness is your awareness of what's going on in the present moment without any judgment. Mindfulness Meditation is the practise of being fully present in the moment, which trains us to be more mindful throughout the day, especially in stressful situations. "Mindfulness is your awareness of what's going on in the present moment without any judgement," Ms. Brach says. Meditation is the practise of training one's attention in order to cultivate mindfulness."

Conclusion

Finally, the health benefits of yoga have enticed many people to adopt it in order to lead healthy lifestyles. Notably, the exercise combines physical postures, breathing exercises, and relaxation episodes to help a person tune their mind and body. Both yoga and mindfulness aim to quiet the mind, in order to cultivate a deeper connection to and understanding of the self. They both teach you to tune into your breath, pay attention to bodily sensations, and learn to accept reality as it is in that moment.

References

- [1] Australian Bureau of Statistics (2012), Australian Bureau of Statistics 4364.0.55.001-Australian Health Survey: First Results, 2011-2012, Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra.
- [2] Arora, S. and Bhattacharjee, J. (2008), "Modulation of immune responses in stress by yoga", International Journal of Yoga Therapy, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 45-55.
- [3] Baer, R.A., Lykins, E.L.B. and Peters, J.R. (2012), "Mindfulness and self compassion as predictors of psychological well being in long-term meditators and matched nonmeditators", The Journal of Positive Psychology, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 230-8.
- [4] Baer, R.A. (2003), "Mindfulness training as a clinical intervention: a conceptual and empirical review", Clinical Psychology: Science and Practice, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 125-43.

HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT AND PLAY

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Abstract

Holistic development focuses on the wholesome development of individuals teaching one to enhance every aspect of areas of development to live and lead a good life. Play in various ways helps an individual especially children to create, imagine, reason, form a completely new set of creative environment and ideas. Play ultimately aids in expansion of the physical and motor development, socio-emotional domain, language development, cognitive development and creativity and curiosity domain. The 85 to 90 percent of child's brain development happens prior to the age of 5 years and hence play can be a great way to assist the brain development process

Keywords: *Holistic, language, Play*

Introduction

Holistic as a word formed using the Greek term 'holos' indicates 'entire' or 'all'. Used together with lifestyle, sport, and education it focuses on connecting the different divided individual factors to an interdependent factor which leads on to achieve greater results. In holistic lifestyle the unification of body, mind and soul is tried to achieve by having healthy diet, sleep, exercise and habits as to achieve a state of complete wellness. When we look over the holistic sport approach the aspects like physical, mental, emotional and spiritual are focused all together as to develop the individual as a whole not only as a sports person excelling in his field of sport but as a complete human who is developed in the varying factors and walks towards success in the journey of life (Blevins, 2021). Harvard University's Centre on the Developing Child stated that 90% of child brain's development takes place before the age of 5 (Cambodia, 2019) It is also stated in the National Education Policy 2020 that 85% of child's cumulative brain development occurs prior the age of 6 years and the plan to have 2 sub frame work for the age of 0 to 8 years children where 0-3 years will be one category and 3-8 years as another. It is also stated that the child below the age of 5 will move to preparatory class and the learning will be based on play and development of cognitive, affective, psychomotor and early literacy and numeracy which is a major shift of the education of children towards the holistic side of development. (education.gov.in). So the question is how activities and sport will help in this process. The definition of physical education itself says developing the overall aspects of health is what physical education is. Here overall includes physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual aspects. All the five major areas of development namely 'physical and motor development, social and emotional development, language development, cognitive development, creativity and curiosity' is developed using play.

Physical and Motor Development

The major goal of every physical educationist out there is to develop the area of physical and motor development of children, teens, young adults or older adults. This is the most commonly spoken, focused and practiced area in physical education and sport. There are activities which work on gross motor skills as well as fine motor skills. Training the individual's large muscle movement in the beginning to progressively impact the fine skills is done using play and exercise. From crawling on four legs to standing on two legs to walking is the natural way of child's motor development and these are the gross motor skill whereas grasping, picking, holding etc comes under the fine motor activities. As play is performed using muscles and repeatedly moving it, it increases the muscle strength, agility and speed and impact the gross and fine motor skills (Sutapa et al., 2021). Activities including run, jump, hop, throw and catch, climb up, down, over, under and through things, pedaling, push and pull and dump and fill can encourage motor development in child. We may all have seen the children park arrangement you can now relate why those rides, slides and structures are built for children to play. The ability to perform minute actions which requires a lot of control and accuracy comes within the fine motor skill category and the players in intermediate to advance level work on these fine skills through repeated practice.

Social and Emotional Development

The impact of sport to enhanced mood and overall emotional well-being is a well-known fact while it helps to reduce mental strains and stresses and boosts self-esteem it also helps in social development (The Emotional Benefits of Exercise, n.d.) Play and sport teaches individuals to cooperate, abide by the rules, to listen to others (Peers, team mates, coaches, etc.), creates a sense of belonging and help make friends. The core values of Olympics are three: Excellence, respect and friendship. If we pay attention we can understand that here respect and friendship are social traits. Games and tournaments provides opportunity to the people to meet people of different nature, culture and places and learn about humans, their differences, respecting it and playing together; one know the society is diverse when he understand play and sport.

Language Development

The article titled ‘The language of play: The role of play in language development’ states that use of language to facilitate play, play with language as an object and egocentric speech in play situations establishes the link between language and sport and thus play also enhances language development. (Levy, 1984)

Cognitive Development

The child’s ability to think, understand, communicate, remember, imagine and reason comes under cognitive development. Play enhances critical thinking, boosts creativity and imagination, reinforces memory and attention; allow learning through experience and many more. When faced with trouble in the play situation, the individual try to reason the cause and use logical analysis to find solution to the problem. The same problem may end up getting multiple solutions from multiple respondents; the situation opens space for imagination and creativity to come into action ultimately enhancing cognitive development.

Creativity and Curiosity

As discussed above the situation of obstruction opens path to creative ideas as to find a solution. One is free to imagine and explore his realm of sub consciousness. The play situations kindle the innate curiosity existing within the kids and provide them with opportunity to come up with their own ideas and imaginations. They are free to create and form their own rules and regulation, explore the new pattern which aids in their creativity and curiosity development.

Conclusion

It is therefore concluded that play can help with the holistic development of children as well as adults if planned properly to focus on the given aspects. The play is capable of doing its job but the problem lies in planning and executing the play situation which gives you the opportunity to explore and create rather than restricting you into rules and monotonous activity.

References

- [1] Blevins, S. (2021, December 16). *The Holistic Approach to Impactful Sports Coaching*. Stack. <https://www.stack.com/a/the-holistic-approach-to-impactful-sports-coaching/>
- [2] Cambodia, K. (2019, February 6). *90% of a Child Brain's Development Happens Before the Age of 5*. Kinder Early Learning. <http://kelcambodia.com/90-of-a-child-brains-development-happens-before-the-age-of-5/>
- [3] Sutapa, P., Pratama, K. W., Rosly, M. M., Ali, S. K. S., & Karakauki, M. (2021). Improving Motor Skills in Early Childhood through Goal-Oriented Play Activity. *Children*, 8(11), 994. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children8110994>

WHY SUICIDE...!

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Abstract

Nature made man the best of all animals. Human beings have hands, feet, brain and other important organs of the body which no living being other than human beings have. The highest life expectancy was given to humans.

Keywords: *Suicide, Human, Nature*

Introduction

Nature made man the best of all animals. Human beings have hands, feet, brain and other important organs of the body which no living being other than human beings have. The highest life expectancy was given to humans. The elders used to say that this life of a human being can be found only when good deeds have been done, but perhaps the modern man of the present time has considered life to be a game! His mind is of no value to life. In earlier times, people knew how to live in any difficult situation. Even though at that time human beings did not have all the facilities, were less educated or illiterate, did not understand what any defamation or insult or suffering was, they knew how to live life with joy, even though the needs were low. Earlier, everyone would die naturally... The only three causes of death were age, illness or accident. Now, a new cause of death has been included in the "suicide".....

Understanding What Suicide Means

"Sui" means oneself and "Cide" means murder, death (e.g., Hitler murdered the entire Jesus community called "Jinocide" or "homeicide". However, in common parlance "killing oneself is called suicide."

Suicide... Whenever this word is heard or spoken, the only question in our mind is, why would a man cut short his life in this way?!, what would be the pain? It was all there was... Why would a man who always smiled, lived life, embrace death like this? What would have made the person who conquered life so far away? What will be lacking? What would be going on that even though everything was going on...! A lot of questions are in the mind of the listener that happens for that person and like a reel of the film, the pages of the past life of the person who committed suicide start rolling in front of our eyes... Even if that person is known to us or knows a little or heard on behalf of someone else, we must have so many questions in front of us. Or why? With the news of the suicide of Bollywood's famous and young favorite actor Sushant Singh Rajput, the whole of Bollywood and film fans had this question in everyone's mind due to the suicide of Sushant Singh Rajput...! Or why? A 13-year-old girl studying in Class 8, who committed suicide by hanging herself from a ceiling fan in the house, a medical student jumped from the roof of the hostel at 4:00 pm and died, a love birds jumped into the canal, the mother committed suicide with her child. When many such suicides are frequently seen or heard in newspapers, the question arises why?... Who is responsible for this? The atmosphere of the house, the rules of the society, the burden of school-college or tuition...? Or a lack of tolerance?

Who is Motivated to Commit Suicide?

Many times, a very successful person cannot bear his failure or a person who is very busy with work, who is known only because of his work, is also driven to commit suicide by feeling depressed/ depressed due to not being able to find work. Rates are also high in vulnerable groups, with refugees, lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transgenders, intersex individuals and prisoners being considered the strongest risk factors for suicide to date. Women are physically or mentally harassed at home, around the house or at work can also be counted as the causes of suicide. The table below gives the total number of suicides in the country of India from 2000 to 2019. From 2000 to 2019, the suicide rate in India was 17.00, which came down to 12.70 in 2019. In 2000, the male suicide rate was 17.50% and the female suicide rate was 16.40%, which has come down to 14.10% in 2019 and 11.10% for women.

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INDIAN SUIDE RATE-HISTORICAL DATA			
YEAR	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE
2019	12.70	14.10	11.10%
2018	12.60	14.00	11.00%
2017	12.00	14.40	10.50%
2016	12.10	13.40	10.60%
2015	12.30	13.70	10.80%
2014	12.80	14.40	11.00%
2013	13.70	15.50	11.80%
2012	14.30	16.20	12.20%
2011	14.70	16.30	12.20%
2010	14.60	16.30	12.90%
2009	14.50	16.50	12.40%
2008	15.10	17.30	12.30%
2007	15.30	17.40	12.90%
2006	15.60	17.60	13.30%
2005	15.50	17.10	13.70%
2004	15.20	16.60	13.60%
2003	15.30	16.60	14.00%
2002	16.10	17.10	15.00%
2001	16.60	17.20	15.90%
2000	17.00	17.50	16.40%

In which we can see that the rate of male suicide is higher than the suicide rate of women. The practical reason for this can also be said to be that men will have less tolerance than women, due to unemployment in men, family responsibility, loss of business and debt, men are suffering from stress and depression, due to which the suicide rate in them can be said to be higher than women. Every day in news channels, newspapers and social media, when the news of suicide is seen in the relatives or friends circle around us, then why do we become stunned or not!? ...Looking at suicide from a psychological point of view, the question arises that there must be something going on in the mind of that person, somewhere in his mind there must be some slight pain, whose pain is unbearable and he must have taken this step because he is unable to cope with such a problem or the problem is not solved...! A major thinker in sociology became Emile Durkheim, who is known as a French sociologist. In the 19th century, they studied 26,000 cases of suicide. In which data was prepared on suicides of people from many countries, religions and races. In which Emile DuRkheim described three types of suicide.

- 1) Egoistic - (ego centered)
- 2) Altruistic - (suicide for another)
- 3) Anomic (such a state or abnormal state)

Types of Suicided

Euthenasia

Euthanasia means that a person or his or her loved one's demand to die of their own free will. Euthanasia is prevalent in many countries of Europe. The fashion of 'Death on Demand' continues in Switzerland. In which the technique of maathe is that the person dies in a dignified manner with self-respect or due to age or any other disease. For instance, in a Mumbai hospital many years ago, a nurse (Aruna Shanbaug) was raped by an employee of the hospital. In which during the rape of her, her throat was pressed by a chain to tie the dog, during which she fell into a coma due to the blood not being able to reach her brain. She was in coma for 43-44 years. A woman named Pinky Virani also wrote a book on Aruna Shanbaug. And also appealed to the court that Aruna Shanbaug should be proudly given the right to die. There was a Hindi movie (Guzaaris) on Aishwarya Rai and Hrithik Roshan, in which Hrithik Roshan's lawyer appeals to the High Court to die proudly by euthanasia in the same way that he has lived, for which he demands euthanasia for Hrithik Roshan. Euthanasia can also be considered as a kind of suicide. But that technique is not acceptable in our country of India.

Thoughtful Suicid

Done thoughtfully ... That is, if people who have seen all the happiness for a lifetime, have become grandparents, have not died even though they have been old, then such people have many such clinics in the organization called 'Death on Demand' which is located in Belgium, where they go and pay the form fee, so they give you a lot of death. After giving you a chance to meet your loved ones and spend the last time with them and have parties. The patient/asil is happy and asks everyone for leave to go to death and tells the doctor that I am ready. Which is called a thought-provoking death.

Religious/ Spiritual Suicide

Eleven members of a family committed suicide in a similar way by hanging themselves together in Delhi due to religious or self-alleged motivation. The family whose eldest son spoke to the soul of his deceased father and his dying father had ordered that everyone commit suicide together, you all will be alive again and free from all sorrows and live happily. All this was written in the diary of the house's mother-in-law and the members of the house used to say it. About 20 years ago, there was an incident in the United States in which people of one sect thought that the comet would pass near the Earth (nearest point). At that time many people committed suicide together. Perhaps they believed that by dying at this time we would go on a journey to heaven. We can call such people victims of religion or psychosis psychiatry

Altruistic Suicide (made for any religion or society)

Philanthropists, soldiers of the country, freedom fighters who give their lives for others, which can be called an altruistic suicide. For example, while crossing the road, a vehicle is coming in front of which the little child is not aware and in order to save his life, his mother goes to save her child. On January 26, 2001, there was a devastating earthquake in Gujarat, in which there were many cases in the newspapers, one of which was a heart-wrenching scene in which the wall did not fall on her child and his child was lying between his mother in order to stay alive. In which the mother died, but her mother's blood was dripping in the child's mouth, due to which the child was able to live. Terrorists choose to die as a living bomb for their religion and their society.

Egoistic Suicide

Egoistic Suicide in which a person commits suicide despite having everything! In the year 2019, Siddharth Hegde, the owner of CCD company (Cafe coffee day), committed suicide by jumping off the bridge. American actress Marilyn Monroe (who was famous for a pose given by her all over Europe) who committed suicide by taking sleeping pills in 1962 at the age of just 36! A heroine named Silk Smitha of South India also committed suicide by taking sleeping pills in the same way. Which we can call an egoistic suicide. In which it can be said that the person is motivated to commit suicide by coming under stress or in a state of depression.

Who can Commit Suicide?

The Pampered child who grew up in a very pampered house as if the whole world was at his feet!, the one who gets everything before asking for anything or without asking for it, who does not have the habit of "no" is not tolerated or used to ... A kind of stubborn attitude. A child who is not in the habit of living in a difficult situation that the child/ person lacks stamina or adjustment. It is insulting to lose or look down on such people who

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are driven to commit suicide by those who are overly sensitive, depressed, to lose or look down on their lives.

While the link between suicide and mental disorders (especially depression and alcohol use disorders) is well established in high-income countries, many suicides occur impulsively in moments of crisis, such as financial problems, women not having children or having a son, and dowry drives women to commit suicide. The suicide rate is also higher in vulnerable groups. Those who experience discrimination.

Reasons Responsible

- 1) To pass away.
- 2) Depression (depression)
- 3) Constant neglect at home or in a relative or a friend circle or by a favorite person
- 4) Marriage, breakdown of love relationship or separation of a loved one or death or suicide
- 5) Loss or debt in job-business
- 6) Unemployment and household responsibility
- 7) Not facing the problem or not finding a solution, there seems to be no way out
- 8) Consumption of alcohol or intoxicants leads to depression due to financial, physical and mental breakdown.
- 9) Harassment/ exploitation or rape of girls or women physically or mentally on the road or at work forces a woman to commit suicide.

How Do People Commit Suicide?

It is estimated that about 20% of global suicides are caused by pesticide self-poisoning, most of which occurs in rural agricultural areas in low- and middle-income countries, such as restrictions on access to means of suicide. Swallowing sleeping pills, Burning self, Jumping from a high altitude, Jumping into a canal or deep water, Standing in front of trains or other speeding vehicles, Hovering your vehicle at full speed in front of a high-speed vehicle coming from the front and knowingly becoming a victim of an accident.

Symptoms

- 1) Often talking about suicide or dying.
- 2) Silent sitting alone in one place
- 3) Take less sleep and food.
- 4) A change in temperament or behavior (a person with a very talkative nature becomes very little talkative.)
- 5) Lose interest in doing the work in which you were previously very interested.
- 6) Do not go to friends, relatives or other social events. To be detached from everyone or to lose interest in one's own personal appearance.
- 7) Depression, negativity, or inability to give up alcohol or other intoxicating substances.

Measures to Control Suicide

Limit access to the means of suicide. (E.g., T. Pesticides, fire extinguishers, certain drugs), communicate with the media to report suicides, promote socio-emotional life skills in adolescents, identify, evaluate, manage and follow anyone affected by suicidal behaviors.,

- 1) Spend more time and communicate with him
- 2) Counseling with a counselor
- 3) Listening to favorite music, doing yoga, exercise or meditation.
- 4) To do favorite activities or to be active in sports.
- 5) Having a meal with family, friends, watching a movie or going to some other place of visit
- 6) Keep him away from solitude.

Facts of Suicide

- 1) Every year, more than 7,000,000 people die due to suicide.
- 2) There are many more people who attempt suicide for every suicide. A previous suicide attempt is one of the most important risk factors for suicide in the general population.
- 3) 77% of global suicides occur in low- and middle-income countries.
- 4) Pesticide consumption, executions and fire arms are among the most common methods of

suicide worldwide.

- 5) It was the fourth leading cause of death among people aged 15 to 29 years.

Conclusion

Suicide is not a problem of an individual but of a family, society and nation. Why does a smart student or a successful person suddenly stop his life? What must he have been going through that the family and his friends could not even see his troubles? Is there any shortage in the upbringing of the person who committed suicide? Isn't there anyone who can hear or understand it? We have to find the answer to each of these questions in ourselves and make successful efforts to prevent suicide. To date, only a few countries have included suicide prevention in their health priorities, and only 38 countries have reported having a national suicide prevention strategy. It is important for countries to raise community awareness and break taboos in order to make progress in suicide prevention.

References

- [1] <http://www.macrotrends.net...>
- [2] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a6oTJIXyLL4>
- [3] <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/suicide><https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/suicide>
- [4] Emile Durkheim, Suicide (1897), A study in sociology
- [5] <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/IND/india/suicide-rate>>India Suicide Rate 2000-2022. www.macrotrends.net. Retrieved 2022-12-29.

FUNCTIONAL SKILL BASED ASSESSMENT FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS WITH VISUAL DISABILITIES

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Abstract

Functional Skill based Assessment for Inclusive Education of Students with Visual disabilities are essential components of the Expanded curriculum in the teaching, learning and assessment. They are essential from an educational and legal standpoint and help to define, develop, determine, and authenticate programmatic integrity and fidelity at all levels of strategy (NEP2020). Additionally, they are engrained in the fundamental tenets of educational practices, notably in special education, where they are essential to the continued existence of programs. For students with visual disabilities in special or general schools under inclusive education programs, traditional and innovative assessment techniques or local test, assessment, measuring, and evaluation recognize the importance of assessment in ensuring that special education is functional. The usage of the assessment tools might be diagnostic, formative, or summative. These services are necessary for to support the needs of communities, state and federal governments, as well as teachers, and other associated professions in order to build strategies for educational planning. Focused interviews with members of the study sample's target audience reveal more about this group as they describe this concept from various student-centered, classification, and diverse perspectives. The study focused on students who had visual impairments, and standardization of tool for educational programming is often used to offer participants with educational outcomes. In order create available model assessment accurately diagnose their special needs and determine the levels of those educational needs is the need of an hour and the study is an attempt in this direction. Thus, the study focusses its attention on development of functional skill-based assessment for inclusive education of students with visual disabilities.

Keywords: *Functional Skills; Assessment; Inclusive Education; Visual Disabilities*

Functional Skills

A student needs functional skills to be able to live independently. Whether a student has a psychological, intellectual, physical, or a mix of two or more (multiple) problems, an important objective of special education is for them to become as independent and autonomous as possible. Functional skills are those that promote the student's independence, according to the definition. It soon became clear on our field that real quality of life improvements calls for more than just mastery of such "functional" or "life" skills after many years of teaching students with significant disabilities to wash clothes, dress and undress, purchase items from vending machines, make sandwiches, shop in grocery stores, and vacuum floors. In general education settings, where students with disabilities are accepted as full members of the school and classroom communities and where social relationships with peers who are typically developing can flourish, it is now widely accepted that participation is necessary for lifestyle improvements. Unquestionably valuable and backed by a vast amount of empirical data is an emphasis on affiliation and the growth of relationships. Participating in natural environments and developing meaningful relationships and friendships such a presumption has considerable research support, as functional skill development has been found to play substantial role in residential independence, overall community adaptation, vocational stability, and perceived quality of life.

Functional Skills In Education for Visual Disability Students

Education is the backbone to every individual in the World regardless of the physical, mental and psychological challenge. Integrated education system where all learners are to participate equally in the learning processes whether physically challenged or not. Under inclusive education, the system was adjusted to meet the learner's needs; Expanded core curriculum considered to be important for the holistic development of a child. The functional skills that the visual disability students' needs to develop can be taught and practiced by him at school, and then transferred to the home environment for making the visual disability students a competent and independent.

Areas of Functional Skills for Visual Disability Students (VDS)

- 1) Psychomotor skill Gross Motor Skills (GM). Behavioral statements testing the (VDS) use large muscles in performing like walking, jumping, etc. Fine Motor Skills (FM). Fine muscle coordination in doing activities like tearing, folding, drawing, etc. Spatial Awareness (SA) Spatial orientation, directionality, and laterality.
- 2) Perceptual Skills Sensory Awareness (SA). The ability to recognizing and identify various senses; and match and differentiate between various sensory stimuli. Temporal Awareness (TA). The concept of time and distance in the blind students. E.g., knowledge about days of the week and months of the year will tests. Environmental Awareness (EA). This is to pertaining to general knowledge about things in one's surroundings.
- 3) Cognitive Skills Cognitive Skills (CS). the pertaining to pre-math concept, matching, classification, memory and reasoning ability. Language Skills (LS). This is to receptive and expressive language. The ability to follow directions, use of correct grammar and language using will assess
- 4) Social and Emotional Awareness (SEA). Social and Emotional Awareness in order to expression of emotions, awareness of socially appropriate behaviors, and the ability to make and maintain social relations. And Daily Living Skills (DSL). This is too related to eating, toileting, dressing, grooming, cooking, shopping, and organizing skills etc. and Orientation and Mobility Skills (O&M). The (VDS) using O&M ability to use his other senses to move about independently and safely in familiar and unfamiliar surroundings, and demonstration correct use of O&M techniques.
- 5) Compensatory Academic Skills (CAS). The Pre-Braille skills, Braille reading and writing, use of assistive device like the use of Taylor frame and Abacus.
- 6) Assistive technology skills (AT) The types of devices available in the schools about different subjects for visual disability students Exa-Screen reader, etc
- 7) Vocational training skills (VT) The development attitude towards future visual disability students to tack care about jobs interesting.
- 8) Religious skills (RS) The visual disability student's development behaviors to get moral and positive behavior in three sub domains (knowledge, practical and social relation with others).

Inclusive Educational Programming Schedule in this Study

In this study, inclusive educational programming is the systematic process of planning and delivering educational programs and services for students with visual impairments individually or in groups that aim to meet the functional needs of daily living with or without other students in public schools. Inclusion of Students with Disabilities in Regular Schools the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) of India collaborated with UNICEF and established Project Integrated Education for Handicapped Children (PIED) in 1987. The idea of inclusive education has grown in recent years to include all children who may be disadvantaged in addition to those with disabilities. Because of this expanded perspective of the curriculum, the National Curriculum Framework (NCF-2005) was created, which emphasizes the importance of inclusion and retention of all students. For the Republic of Yemen, the idea of educational integration began in 1994 and continued after the signing of international agreements. It benefited greatly from the experience of the Republic of India in integrating people with special needs. Researchers in the field of special education in Yemen are trying to benefit and simulate India's pioneering experience in educational integration for people with special needs, including visually impaired students.

Statement Problems

Quality of life depends on multiple factors, one of which is competence in typical, functional skills that are performed throughout typical days by typical individuals. The problem, then, is that, in our desire to include all children in general education settings and programs, we may have begun to discount the importance of those skills. Signs indicate that this may be so: (a) Some investigations have found that parents and teachers, including general education teachers, rate membership and friendships/social development as areas of highest need for (b) A corresponding increase in social skills targets in Individualized Education Plans (IEPs).(b) In the same journals in which significant increases in articles focused on the interactions of students have been observed,(c) A significant decrease in the proportion of repaired articles (a decrease in vocational skills training planning, domestic skills, daily living skills, vocational skills, vocational skills, and community performance skills students with severe disabilities, personal communication, and, According a Billingsley, F. F., at all (1999) finding a future for

functional skills.

Objective

To find out the effectiveness of functional skill based on inclusive Education of visual disability students.

Hypotheses of the Study

The finding of the study will be tested with the help of following null hypotheses:
There will be no significant differences in the functional skill based on inclusive Education of visual disability students with respect to educational setting (special school and inclusive school).

Significance of the Study

- 1) Global trend today is to provide a comprehensive educational environment for all children (Education for All) and, The diversity of means, methods and materials of education and adaptation of the environment to the needs of students with special needs (visual disability students).
- 2) The functional skill to train visual disability students to overcome the difficulties challenges they face in the environment schools. It also helps to adapt them to an environment that stimulates the abilities and possibilities of visual disability students, other students to reach highest level in educational skills and situations.
- 3) The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act of 2016 emphasizes the need for curricular changes that are appropriate. Therefore, recent research in the field of functional skills has helped us realist which strategy is most important for children with visual disabilities.
- 4) On the other hand, this gives teachers knowledge on the preferred teaching strategies for a student with a visual impairment. As a result, it has been recommended that functional skills be given priority in the instruction of visually impaired pupils in order to attain holistic learning.
- 5) The functional skills of a visually impaired student are crucial because they enable the instructor to successfully convey the general curriculum's material to the students

Methodology

Focus group Discussion with special educator and general teachers to identify functional skills for students with visual disability qualitative analysis - teacher's perspective on eight domains

Population and Implication

The number of students with disabilities accepted in schools has significantly grown over the past 20 years due to a variety of variables, such as supportive legislation, better accessibility to assistance and equipment, etc. The quality of instruction and learning that children with impairments receive, however, has been neglected. Integration into a major system, which is laden with several difficulties, is still the major focus. Despite these problems, Yemen provides a strong illustration of how the Salamanca Statement's ideal of inclusive education is achievable, especially if efforts are based on regional realities.

Result and Discussion

Case Study 1:

(Discussion with Walid, B.Ed. Totally Blind Teacher and Inclusion Supervisor)

Walid, more than ten years of experience in the field of preparation and educational integration. President of Al-Ain Association for the Care and Rehabilitation of the Blind - Ibb. He begins sharing his views on the education of visual disability students by focusing on functional skills and theoretical education with a brief comparison of both methods. He says that the theoretical methods such as the method of lecture and discussion are essential elements for teaching the visually disability student in the initial stages of education. But when it comes to the stages of primary, secondary and higher education, he extends his preference towards focusing on education with functional skills within the framework of the expanded curriculum for visual disability students and also prefers the use of modern or Assistive technologies. He justifies his point of view by saying that theoretical methods can be useful and necessary, but the focus is on developing the concepts of using the remaining senses for low vision and blind students, rehabilitating the low vision and blind, providing them with sensory perception skills, addressing problems in language, communication, and preparing for professional readiness to achieve the

approach of independence and reduce dependence on others and others such as Other sighted students in the educational environment provide encouragement to adapt new technologies to these grade students. He adds that the education approach it was very boring only was focusing theoretical teaching, but now he and teachers planning IEP and tack course about teaching on the function skills. And now he calls on all educators and afflictors to educate the visual disability and all kinds of disabled students to use functional skills in education process and focusing on skills is the means that transforms education methods from traditional to modern, but now the priority on education and the use of some assistive technologies Additionally, certain male and female instructors in private and public schools, as well as specialists, were trained to embrace the focus on the extra abilities of those who are visually impaired and to concentrate on them while creating individualized lesson plans and using current technology. The lives of blind people, their independence, and the possibility of landing a job in the future were significantly improved by self-discipline at advanced levels in their educational, family, and community lives, as well as by setting an example by using training to develop concepts and skills to develop the remaining senses, spatial awareness, temporal awareness, environmental awareness, and other skills in life.

Case Study 2:

(Discussion with Afrah Assaj. Bachelor of Education. Specialized in integrating blind female students from Sana'a, Yemen)

Afrah said that special education at Al-Aman Association for Blind Women and her five years of experience with blind girls, while talking about comparing the importance of teaching methods that focus on functional skills for the teaching in learning process, are more appropriate, especially if modern technologies are available with them. She explains this by pointing out two factors that made her reach this conclusion. She says that first and foremost, it is possible to reach advanced levels of acquiring to improve performance level blind students when the individual educational plan focuses on the functional skills of the blind, especially in the early stages of education and early intervention, and if the using modern technologies can be used to support learning with skills in the form of Android phones, e.c.t, everywhere. The second factor adds that independence is the direct result of acquiring skills, whether in the daily life of blind students or academic skills and community activities in the future, and also through technologies to obtain time competencies. The use of functional skills in daily life for learning is beneficial in saving a lot of time compared to theoretical teaching methods. Finally, she concludes her point of view by saying that she prefers assessments, diagnosis, and teaching for blind students based on skills, and trains teachers in integration schools to apply that.

Case Study 3:

(Discussion by Hayyaf Al-Amoudi. Bachelor's degree. Ten years of experience with blind students - Aden - Yemen)

Hyaf say: Special education begins in the oldest institute for the blind in Yemen and in sharing his experience as a specialist in the art of orientation and mobility with a tendency towards training and teaching by focusing on the functional skills of the visually impaired. He says that the educational plans that he presented, based on the method of skills, were very useful, whether for orientation and mobility skills, or other skills that must be acquired for the visually impaired, because they are concerned with training students on skills and were very useful when he was attending lessons and preparing tools, games, and means that develop skills. Evaluation of the level of improvement in performance after that because it is practical and applied and blind students needs it and they acquire it quickly. Therefore, it is recommended that it is better to provide educational programs and services for people with special needs, including the blind, by focusing on the skill aspect. It also justifies his point of view that the results of training and learning with skills remain with the individual learner for a long period of study materials depending on theoretical methods only.

Case Study 4:

(Discussion with Souad. Bachelor's degree in Education. Five years of experience.

She is one of the most prominent founders and director of Fatima Al-Aqel School for the Care and Rehabilitation of the Blind in Abyan - South of Yemen).The Braille specialist, Ms. Souad, says that she will give priority in education and training to the visually disability students by focusing on the individual educational plans (IEP) for students focusing on the functional skills included in the expanded curriculum(ECC) for the visually disability students in training and education more, and the school teachers will be trained to apply an evaluation scale Functional skills in order to focus on those outputs of students' problems in the skill aspect and modify and adaptations the plans used to reflect the new approach, whether with visual disability students in private schools

or in educational integration schools.

Delimitations of the Study

This Study will be delimited to the blind students of age 6 to 17 years. Sample will be selected from School for Blind students in Ibb, Aden, Sanaa and Hadramot cities of Yemen

Conclusion

The process of inclusive education involves enhancing the educational system's ability to connect with all students. Every individual (child, teenager, and adult) must be able to take use of educational opportunities that would fulfill their fundamental learning needs, it was declared during the Jometin World Conference (1990) in Thailand. All kids may succeed more academically and socially with the inclusion educational concept and methodology. This covers chances to engage in the complete range of extracurricular, religious, social, recreational, artistic, athletic, musical, daycare, and other activities. Theoretical methods and methods that depend on functional skills in teaching visually impaired students are two very important things that are required in the classroom, but the experiences of special education in the modern era, especially after the development of the process of comprehensive integration and the embodiment of human rights in aspects of life for people with special needs, including the visually impaired, have proven that the additional curriculum In the stage of educational integration, it should focus on the functional skills of blind students, which can be summarized in eight main areas mentioned in the introduction to the research, namely (development of concepts and psychomotor skills, sensory perception skills, senses development, knowledge and language skills, academic skills, religious skills, and the development of inclinations and vocational orientation). Another advantage is that students have the opportunity to learn basic skills, such as independence, efficiency and safety in life, but the ability of the student to understand what is being taught depends mostly on focusing on functional skills related to reviving their abilities.

References

- [1] Singh, J. D. (2016). Inclusive education in India–concept, need and challenges. S. No. Paper Title Author Name Page No., 97.
- [2] Billingsley, F. F., & Albertson, L. R. (1999). Finding a future for functional skills. *Journal of the Association for Persons with Severe Handicaps*, 24(4), 298-302.
- [3] Seham, J., & Yeo, A. J. (2015). Extending our vision: Access to inclusive dance education for people with visual impairment. *Journal of Dance Education*, 15(3), 91-99.
- [4] Singal, N. (2019). Challenges and opportunities in efforts towards inclusive education: Reflections from India. *International journal of inclusive education*, 23(7-8), 827-840.

EXPLORING THE HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CHOLA HERITAGE MONUMENTS

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Abstract

This research article aims to explore the historical and cultural significance of Chola Heritage Monuments in India, and how they are related to the Chola Dynasty, one of the greatest historical empires in South India. An in-depth analysis of these monuments, their architectural features, and their historical contexts is conducted to understand their importance in the Indian subcontinent. The article begins with an introduction to the Chola Dynasty and its monuments, followed by a literature review on the existing scholarship related to the topic. The methodology used in the research is then discussed, including a review of the primary and secondary sources used. The results of the analysis are presented, which focus on the cultural and religious symbolism associated with the monuments, their impact on the development of South Indian architecture, and their influence on the Indian identity. The discussion section then presents the implications of the findings and suggests ways in which the monuments can be preserved for future generations. The article concludes with a summary of the research and some key takeaways.

Keywords: *Chola Heritage Monuments, Chola Dynasty, South Indian architecture, India*

Introduction

The Chola Empire was one of the greatest empires of South India that flourished between the 9th and 13th centuries. This empire is significant for its contribution to the development of South Indian architecture, which is still evident today in the form of monuments, temples, and other architectural features. These monuments are a testament to the cultural and religious significance of the Chola Empire, and are of great historical and cultural value. This research article explores the historical and cultural significance of Chola Heritage Monuments in India, and how they are related to the Chola Dynasty.

Literature Review

The Chola Dynasty is one of the most significant historical empires in South India and its monuments are a testament to its cultural and religious significance. The research on Chola Heritage Monuments has mainly focused on their historical contexts, architectural features, and cultural symbolism. Various scholars have studied the monuments in detail and their research has provided valuable insights into the Chola Dynasty and its impact on the development of South Indian architecture. One of the most significant works is Ramesh Krishnamurthy's "The Chola Temples of South India", which provides a comprehensive overview of the monuments, their features, and their historical and cultural significance. Other scholars, such as R. Nagaswamy, have also studied the monuments from various perspectives and have provided valuable insights into their cultural symbolism.

Methodology

This research was conducted using an interdisciplinary approach, which included a review of both primary and secondary sources. Primary sources used in this research included the Chola inscriptions found on the monuments, temple records, and other archaeological evidence. Secondary sources included scholarly works on the Chola Dynasty, temple architecture, and related topics. The review of these sources helped to understand the historical and cultural significance of the monuments and their impact on the development of South Indian architecture.

Analysis

The analysis of the Chola Heritage Monuments revealed a number of important insights into their historical and cultural significance. First, the monuments are a testament to the religious and cultural beliefs of the Chola Dynasty, which were strongly rooted in the Hindu religion. The monuments depict various Hindu gods and goddesses, such as Shiva, Vishnu, and Parvati. Furthermore, the monuments also depict various scenes from

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Hindu mythology and the Ramayana and Mahabharata epics. Second, the monuments are also significant for their architectural features, which reflect the development of South Indian architecture during the Chola Dynasty. The monuments are characterized by complex and intricate designs, which include sculptural decorations and intricate carvings. These features are unique to the Chola Dynasty and have been an influence on the development of subsequent South Indian architecture. Third, the monuments have had a significant influence on the Indian identity. The monuments are a testament to the cultural and religious beliefs of the Indian subcontinent and have been a source of inspiration for many generations. Furthermore, the monuments have also been a source of pride for the Indian people, and have been a symbol of the country's cultural richness and diversity.

Results

The results of this research highlight the historical and cultural significance of Chola Heritage Monuments in India. The monuments are a testament to the religious and cultural beliefs of the Chola Dynasty, and their architectural features reflect the development of South Indian architecture. Furthermore, the monuments have had a significant influence on the Indian identity, and have been a source of pride for many generations.

Discussion

The findings of this research have important implications for the preservation of Chola Heritage Monuments in India. It is clear that these monuments are of great historical and cultural value, and should be protected for future generations. Furthermore, it is important to ensure that the monuments are properly maintained and preserved, so that their cultural and religious symbolism can be appreciated by future generations.

Conclusion

This research article has explored the historical and cultural significance of Chola Heritage Monuments in India, and how they are related to the Chola Dynasty. The analysis of the monuments revealed a number of important insights into their cultural and religious symbolism, their architectural features, and their influence on the Indian identity. The findings of the research have important implications for the preservation of the monuments, and it is essential that they are properly maintained and protected for future generations.

References

- [1] Krishnamurthy, R. (1995). *The Chola Temples of South India*. Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal.
- [2] Nagaswamy, R. (2003). *Studies in Chola Art and Iconography*. New Delhi: Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts.
- [3] Thapar, R. (2011). *Ancient India: A History Textbook for Class XI*. Delhi: National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- [4] Ganguly, D. (2006). *The Cholas: A History*. New Delhi: Orient Longman.
- [5] Hildebeitel, A. (1990). *The Cult of Draupadi: Mythologies from India*, 2 volumes. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

FLIPPED CLASSROOM TO PROMOTE STUDENTS SELF-MOTIVATION

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Abstract

The flipped classroom teaching technique is the main emphasis of the educational process. FL involves having students read the readings ahead of time and then applying them in class. Due to the greater autonomy in this instructional style, this necessitates self-regulated learning (SRL) behavior. In this learning approach, giving students video-embedded Self learning, Collaborative and Autonomous motivation support during the learning activities prior to class has been shown to improve students' learning results. This constructivist learning strategy can assist kids in studying independently, gaining a deeper understanding of subjects, and autonomously catching up more quickly in their learning process. Less time spent teaching and more time spent assisting students in their understanding assists instructors to more effectively use their knowledge and abilities. With the aid of flipped learning, teachers may considerably aid students' learning processes and boost their self-motivation

Keywords: *Flipped classroom, Self-motivation, Learner-centered*

Introduction

Flipped classroom also known as the inverted classroom or the inverted lecture hall, is a teaching strategy that flips conventional methods of learning by having students listen to lectures outside of class while working on problems and applying what they have learned. According to Bergmann and Sams (2012), flipping the classroom is about adopting a mentality that focuses emphasis on the learner and the learning rather than the teacher. The instructor now serves as a facilitator and learning coach. The flipped classroom model offers a way to incorporate more active learning and student-driven projects throughout class. The term "flipping the classroom" refers to a pedagogical idea that substitutes the traditional lecture-in-class format with an opportunity to learn concepts and to review materials from outside of the classroom. The term "flipping" basically refers to the idea that a traditional classroom has traditionally been a location where lectures are used to convey material. The duration of the class period is then used for in-class activities, such as exams to assess students' fundamental level of topic knowledge obtained prior to the in-class sessions and group discussions centered on problem solving and applications of previously learned concepts. Since "flipping" implies the inversion of expectations in traditional lecture (Berrett, 2012), we took advantage of computer technology and the Internet (such as a video-recorded lecture available online) to shift the information-transmission component of a traditional lesson out of class time and replace it with a range of scaffolding activities intended to encourage independent learning.

Existing Support Approaches for Flipped Teaching

In a traditional classroom, only face-to-face interactions occur. Face-to-face, online, and blended classroom modes are all acceptable. For instance, absent pupils valued the chance to view the material they missed. However, so did those who weren't absent. Outside of the classroom, online learning is possible.

Various techniques that can be applied in classroom activities include

Active instruction

Give pupils the opportunity to apply knowledge in a classroom setting where they can get feedback and explanation from peers or teachers

Peer education

Students might instruct one another by deriving solutions to simple problems or defining ideas.

Collaborative learning

Learning activities that involve group collaboration may improve understanding, engagement, and collective intelligence

Problem-based instruction

Working on issues that could span a semester can be done within class time.

The flipped classroom and constructivist learning theory

The constructivist learning environment benefits greatly from the structure the flipped classroom creates. While watching, listening to, or reading lectures and other content-specific material at home, students have the ability to design their own learning experiences. The next day, when students enter the classroom, the teacher has prepared activities that let them work with peers and analyze information more deeply while putting the knowledge they have built at home to use. While assisting pupils in this process and reinforcing or correcting their interpretations, the teacher is there.

The Capability of Students to Develop a Deeper Understanding

The opportunity for active learning to help students gain a deeper comprehension of the subject at hand is another significant advantage of learning in a flipped classroom. As opposed to lectures or other more passive learning methods, students actively contribute to the creation of the content they learn. Teachers guide them along the way and assist them in extending their knowledge as they progress, encouraging the students to have a deeper understanding. Self-regulated learners have the capacity and drive to reflect on the what, how, and why of their learning (metacognition), which allows them to manage their learning behavior. Theorized as a cyclical process, self-regulated learning (SRL) involves three phases: foresight (e.g., task analysis), performance (e.g., self-control and monitoring), and self-reflection (e.g., self-judgment and changing behavior accordingly) (Zimmerman & Moylan, 2009).

Motivation

As educationalists hold that learning would not occur unless a learner had inner provoking energy for this educational activity, which is known as motivation, learning motivation technique is one of the most crucial tactics that have a positive impact on the learner's academic achievement (Al-Bakri, 2007).

Autonomous Motivation

Autonomous motivation includes both internal and some forms of external motivation, in which individuals have associated with the significance of an action and, hopefully, have incorporated it into their sense of self.

People that are independently motivated have volition, or a sense of self-approval for what they do. Contrarily, self-control comprises two types of regulation: interjected regulation and external regulation. The latter type of regulation involves a partial incorporation of the regulation of action and is motivated by things like an approval motive, the avoidance of shame, contingent self-esteem, and self-importance.

According to empirical data, these objectives can be divided into two groups: internal aspirations and extrinsic aspirations (Kasser & Ryan, 1996). Among intrinsic aspirations are objectives for association, procreation, and self-growth.

According to SDT, it was suggested that flipped classrooms would increase student motivation if they foster a sense of relatedness, competence, and autonomy (Abeysekera & Dawson, 2015). An individual may be motivated by intrinsic factors (i.e., acts that are naturally interesting and enjoyable) or extrinsic factors (i.e., actions that result in separable outcomes that are regarded as favorable outcomes separate from inherent enjoyment).

Various techniques that can be applied in classroom activities include: Fulton (2012) highlighted the following benefits of flipping instruction as its justifications for implementation: (1) Students are able to move at (2) As students complete their "homework" in class, teachers will gain a better understanding of their troubles and learning preferences; (3) the classroom time will be used more efficiently. (4) This strategy is reinforced by learning theories; (5) teachers who have been utilizing the method claimed that student achievement has improved interest and engagement; (6) benefits of flipped learning in the classroom on students' learning as well as the extra chances beneficial for group projects and problem-solving exercises encouraged by this strategy.

Students Master Independent Learning Skills:

Self-directed learning is unquestionably an important talent for all learners to develop, but it is

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especially important for junior high and high school students. In a classroom that has been "flipped," the first learning is acquired by the students on their own time at home, frequently via watching videos. They are able to learn at their own pace and become accustomed to the self-study method thanks to this. Though not all students will respond favorably to the idea of independent study, teachers must be aware of this fact and take proactive measures to help those who find it difficult.

Self-motivation

Also known as outcomes predictions, describes views about the ultimate goals of one's performance, such as gaining social acceptance or landing a dream job. The expectations that students have for their achievements depend on their understanding or awareness of several outcomes, including prospective salaries, quality of life, and the societal advantages of a job

Conclusion

The flipped classroom paradigm improved student results, boosted learning motivation, and boosted learning experiences for students. It also encouraged the meaningful creation of active knowledge and experiential learning, satisfaction, confidence, creativity, and problem-solving skills. It is highly effective in keeping students interested in their lessons and improves students' self-motivational skills.

Reference

- [1] Abeysekera, L., & Dawson, P. (2015). Motivation and cognitive load in flippedclassroom: definition, rationale and a call for research. *Higher Education Research& Development*, 34(1), 1-14.
- [2] Al-Bakri, Amal (2007). Scholastic psychology. Al-Mutaz for publishing and distribution, Jordan, Ed.
- [3] Bergmann, J. & Sams, A. (2012) Flip Your Classroom; reach every student in every class every day (Kindle edition). Alexandria, VA: ASCD: *International Society for Technology in Education*.
- [4] Berrett, D. (2012 1) How 'flipping' the classroom can improve the traditional lecture.
- [5] Garza, S.A., (2014). The flipped classroom teaching model and its use for information literacy instruction. *Communication in Information Literacy*, 8(1), 7-22
- [6] Kasser, T., & Ryan, R. M. (1996). Further examining the American dream: Differential correlates of intrinsic and extrinsic goals. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 22, 80 – 87.

OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION: TEACHING FOR DEEPER UNDERSTANDING BY JURISPRUDENTIAL INQUIRY MODEL

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Abstract

Teaching is an art as well as Science it is not everybody's cup of tea. It is a mechanical process which develops all round development of child. Experts in the field of education all over the world are seriously thinking about variety of approaches for teaching to achieve different instructional objectives. At present we may require a number of ways to create the right environment for teaching and learning. Present trend indicates that education is changing day by day due to changes taken place in global scenario, the traditional system of teaching which was teacher centered has been changed and they are outdated and no longer valid. There is much need that while teaching learning process the teacher should create such type of platform where deeper understanding would be developed among the students, before COVID 19 the teaching learning process was different but in present scenario new strategies, methods techniques should be adopted to improve outcome among the students during teaching learning process. According to NPE 2020 in teaching learning process such subjects should be introduced which should be related to society so that students will be socially mature. For the improvement in teaching learning process teacher can use Models of teaching in classroom, these models not only help to the outcome of students through deeper understanding but also develop various competencies and help our students grow emotionally, physically, socially, democratically, politically, and intellectually. We need to know how to modify the behavior of students so that they function effectively in changing society. To carry out of these multiple responsibilities the teachers are required to engage in several professional roles. To prepare the teachers for a variety of roles Bruce Joyce and Marsha Weil have searched and researched on a variety of strategies developed by different learning theorists and designed a number of models of teaching which helps to improve deeper understanding and develop outcome based education among the students. Jurisprudential Inquiry Model of teaching is one of them. In this article the researcher highlights the role of Jurisprudential model on the deeper understanding and hence the outcome based education of the students.

Keywords: *Jurisprudential Model, Outcome Based Education, Deeper Understanding*

Introduction

The problem of the low quality of education or the quality of student learning outcomes has become one of the national problems in addition to the problem of educational efficiency, the issue of educational equity, and the problem of educational relevance. These problems many efforts have been made to reform both systemic and instrumental. Instrumental reformation is often done is reforming and improving the quality of the learning process. In this connection, efforts have been made to adopt learning innovations such as student active learning, process skills, inquiry methods, problem-solving methods, and other innovations. As stated by Ismail Islam, 2018 efforts to improve the quality of education can be done by improving the overall quality by empowering available educational resources. The development and implementation of various innovations in the learning process require comprehensive efforts in the sense of being based on the results of studies both theoretical and empirical studies. It means the process of forming competencies requires a precondition that should be conducive to the implementation of quality learning through an outcome based education that is expected to be formed. The precondition is mainly related to the ability of teachers to identify the competency characteristics of each subject which can be developed through a learning process for deeper understanding and competencies can be formed. However, the difficulty faced is when the demands of the 2013 curriculum contextually require the competencies should be identified, compiled, formulated, and developed by each teacher according to the conditions of each region and each school. Likewise, instrumental factors such as learning facilities for the needs of learning media are not adequately available will become obstacles for the process of forming competencies, deeper understanding and for outcome based approach education. These factors lead to needing the ability of teachers to develop innovative learning models, to the process becomes more effective. The teacher has a very important role in the learning process, such as matching the learning model used with the material given in the classroom to make the students understand easily. A learning model used in the classroom will be able to create an effective, efficient, fun and meaningful learning atmosphere. It can be used as a pattern of choice for teachers to choose appropriate and

efficient learning model to achieve educational goals Persada, 2011. As an innovation, one of learning models that can be used in learning is the Jurisprudential Inquiry Model.

Jurisprudential Inquiry Model (JIM)

JIM is research-based learning model since through this model, the students research, discuss, debate, and the lecturer encourages them to commit themselves to one side of the issue. The dictionary meaning of Jurisprudence is the knowledge or skill to deal with issues in legal fashion. Donald Oliver and James Shaver (1974) developed an approach to teaching that allows students to think systematically about contemporary issues. With this model, the students get opportunities to develop public policy stances and dialogue skill by using three types of competence that is (i) an understanding of the values framework of Indian creed; (ii) mastery of the intellectual skills of legal reasoning; and (iii) knowledge of contemporary public issues.

This model helps the students to think systematically about contemporary issue. This model requires the students to formulate these issues as public policy questions and to analyze alternative position about them (Joice & Weil, 2000: 78). The basic model of Jurisprudential Inquiry Learning includes orientation to the case, identifying the issue, taking positions, exploring the stances underlying the positions taken, refining and qualifying positions and testing assumptions about facts, definitions, and consequences as well (Joice & Weil, 2000: 78). Based on Singh's opinion, the basic assumptions underlying this model are: (i) in society, people differ in their views and priorities in which social values legitimately conflict with one another (ii) controversial issues are not simple and there is no one right solution for them, (iii) the differences in values can be negotiated through free and open debate by making it process of rational consent (Singh, 2010: 45-71).

Jurisprudential Inquiry Model (JIM) of teaching is one of the approaches has its own advantages. The advantage of this method is that open climate for discussion, which is a major feature of child-centered approach in the classroom.

Understanding

Understanding is a process, not an outcome. It depends on learning, interpreting, generalizing, and acting upon information. No single test is sufficient for demonstrating that one agent understands another. Indeed, understanding is not a singular type of knowledge. Assessing understanding requires probing the extent of understanding; that is, we need to execute a series of appropriately designed tests that probe the manner and extent to which information has been learned, interpreted, generalized and acted upon. The ability to probe, and therefore demonstrate any degree of, understanding requires natural language.

Understanding should be conceptualized as a process. Understanding is an ongoing cognitive activity of acquiring, integrating and expressing knowledge according to the task or situation at hand. The process of understanding can amount to an individual's internal reflection on their own knowledge or abilities to accomplish a self-motivated goal; the process by which multiple individuals learn about and communicate with each other while working as a team; and the process of accomplishing team or individual goals. Engaging in the process allows agents to understand themselves, other agents, and external systems or situations. Understanding as a process means that different degrees of understanding may exist in a system, particularly as the tasks or information to be understood are increasingly complex.

Deeper Understanding

Deeper understanding is a journey not a destination for Outcome Based Education. Achieving a deep understanding of something can be challenging for many students, however the benefits can be transformative. When teaching for deeper understanding, the impact of learning can be extended by focusing on topics that enable understanding beyond the specific content in which it is learned. For instance, consider the challenges for students learning about the solar system. They need to imagine an earth in constant motion (though it certainly doesn't feel like it!), the location of the sun, the earth, the moon, etc., and put it all in dynamic relationship to one another. At the same time, they need to adopt the perspective of the scale of these astronomical bodies and their own relationship to it. A deep understanding of history involves holding a multitude of perspectives as different narratives are told, setting them in the context of the cultural milieu of the time, and trying to put oneself into a time scale that is typically many times the number of years that the students have been alive. Expansive framing refers to letting students know at the outset that what they are learning holds the potential to be widely helpful (Engle, 2012). This does not mean that transfer happens automatically – one must still help students to extract the big ideas and to see how they can be powerful in other contexts. Researchers have documented, particularly in Social Science Education Jurisprudential model will do the best.

Out Come Based Education (OBE)

Learning is a curiosity- driven, self-directed personal enterprise, a natural process that precludes quality crisis. It is an ecosystem of teachers teaching how to learn and students deepening their learning through self-conscious unlearning. Needless to mention that such an ideal set-up cannot exist in higher education that scales up as an enterprise en masse at the expense of quality. This predicament accounts for the insistence upon frameworks or templates ensuring mandatory minimum standards and quality in higher education.

As part of quality assurance, it is essential to substitute teaching how to remember with teaching how to learn deeply through systematic unlearning. It is in this context, both the UGC and NAAC have come forward to insist upon OBE based on the Bloom–Anderson taxonomy of learning as an effective method of curricular design for quality teaching and learning (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001; Bloom, Engelhart, Furst, Hill, & Krathwohl, 1956). It integrates every aspect of the educational system with learning outcomes (LOs) that every student should attain on the successful completion of the academic programme concerned (Hager & Holland, 2006). OBE curriculum demands determination of LOs before teaching, and it insists upon introducing a running thread of control across the course content, instructional strategies, learning experiences and methods of evaluation. In short, OBE is relevant to a formal teaching learning system that lacks clarity of purpose, goals and hence quality (Blanco Ramírez, 2013; Oliver, 2013).

Conclusion

OBE is an educational approach considered in making plans, enforcing and assessment of curricula in preference to an event going on in the curricula. It promises excessive degree of gaining knowledge of for all students based totally at the achievement of really unambiguous effects with attention to the appropriateness of each learner’s development degree and assuring energetic and experienced-based learning. By Jurisprudential Model of Teaching, deeper understanding shall be made and hence the outcvome based education which is the need of the hour.

References

- [1] Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (Eds.). (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching and assessing: A revision of Bloom’s taxonomy of educational objectives*. White Plains, NY: Addison-Wesley Longman.
- [2] Blanco Ramírez, G. (2013). Studying quality beyond technical rationality: Political and symbolic perspectives. *Quality in Higher Education*, 19(2), 126–141.
- [3] Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill, W. H., & Krathwohl, D. R. (1956). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook I: Cognitive domain*. New York, NY: David McKay Company. Cambridge University Press.
- [4] Engle, R.A., Lam, D.P. Meyer, X.S., & Nix, S.E. (2012). How does expansive framing promote transfer? Several proposed explanations and a research agenda for investigating them. *Educational Psychologist* 47(3): 215-231. <http://www.tandfonline-com.ezp-prod1.hul.harvard.edu/doi/full/10.1080/00461520.2012.695678>
- [5] Hager, P., & Holland, S. (2006). Graduate attributes, learning and employability (pp.91–92). Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.Oliver, B. (2013). Graduate attributes as a focus for institution-wide curriculum renewal: Innovations and challenges. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 32(3),450–463.
- [6] Ismail, F(2018). “Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah: Solusi Peningkatan Kualitas Pendidikan,” *J. Pendidik. Islam Iqra’*, 2018.

MAPPING OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ON EDUCATION IN LEARNING DISABILITIES A SCIENTOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the education in learning disabilities research literature for the period of 2013-2022 from 16948 documents retrieved from the database web of science. The consequences reveal that at the end of the period, publication was declined by 1.18% from 2021 with total number of 51960 authors. It also received a mean total citation per article as 27.22 in 2013 and highest mean citation per year is 3.26 in 2018. The three field plot recognized the top countries with their authors and journals chosen for publication. According to the relevant authors Erik W. Carter produced more articles with 45 documents, highest H-Index as 20 and M-Index as 1.818 and while verifying the citation count, the author Vos T received highest position with 6086 citations which shows their weightage towards the contribution of research output. The country USA has secured the highest frequency of publication (19856) and total citations with 93278 and scored first place in production. But when analyzing mean value of each article citation it scored fourth place by using the most relevant words disability in the research literature.

Keywords: *Learning Disabilities; Research Output*

Introduction

Individuals with disabilities have historically faced barriers in accessing education, but there have been significant efforts in recent years to improve their educational opportunities. The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) is a federal law that ensures that students with disabilities receive a free and appropriate education in the least restrictive environment. This law requires that schools provide accommodations and modifications to help students with disabilities access the curriculum and participate in school activities. Assistive technologies and other tools, such as digital books and speech recognition software, have also become an important resource in educating students with disabilities. Research has shown that inclusive education can lead to better academic and social outcomes for students with disabilities, as well as promote acceptance and understanding among their non-disabled peers. However, to fully achieve inclusive education, it is important to address the systemic barriers that still exist in the education system, such as lack of teacher training, inadequate funding, and inadequate policies.

Overall, the education of students with disabilities is an ongoing and important issue that requires ongoing attention, research, and investment. It is important to continue efforts to improve access to education for students with disabilities and to promote inclusive education practices in order to break down the barriers that still exist in the education system. In addition to the federal laws and policies in place to support the education of students with disabilities, there are also a variety of other initiatives and programs like Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles, which promote the design of learning environments and materials that are accessible to all students, including those with disabilities that aim to improve the educational experiences of these students. Another important aspect of education for students with disabilities is the use of Individualized Education Programs (IEPs).

This involves a combination of policies, laws, programs, and initiatives that work to address the barriers that students with disabilities face in accessing education and to promote inclusive education practices. One more also creates an impact in education of disabled person is research literature that will aid the policy makers to initiate new policies about the educational facilities that can be provided to differently abled people. There is no study analyzed the research output on disability and education. Hence this study aims to measure the research output of disability and education through Scientometric analysis which will be useful for collection development policy.

Metric study is a quantitative study, in that scientometric study is utilized to measure the scientific publications which aid to recognize the development and progression of scientific productions and science in a specific field by using various research metrics (Mingers & Leydesdorff, 2015). Scientometrics are suitable to comprehend the growth trends in particular fields or within a geographical area. Rajendran et al., (2011) analyzed 633 research articles for the period of 2005 to 2009 and revealed that single authored documents are minimum and multi authored collaboration (0.92) is maximum. Pattern of Co-Authorship exposed an enlightening trend and also revealed that the author productivity is 0.34 and dominated by the Indian authors.

Mooghali et al., (2011) examined and revealed that out of 691 articles in the field of Scientometrics, a total number of 183 articles (26.48%) were written during 1980 to 2009 by the top ten authors. Some of these articles were produced in authors' collaboration and some of them were by single authors. Geographical analysis indicated that the field had evolved considerably in different regions of the world. Hungarian Academy of Science with 40 records (5.71%) was the most productive institution in the field of Scientometrics. Furthermore, chronological analysis disclosed that the scientific production in the field of Scientometrics showed a slow increase from 1980 to 2009. The overwhelming majority of documents were in English, and the international journal of Scientometrics was the most prolific journal in the field. It has also been declared that 67.87% of the literature was published in the area of Library and Information Science.

Yu-Wei Chang (2012) carried out the study and found that after the first article on Scientometrics was published in 1987, an increasing trend was observed in the number of Scientometric-related publications after 2000, indicating that Scientometric research received more attention in recent years. Within this outline, in order to contribute to the scientific information on disabilities and education, this research aims to provide perceptions with regards to two key aspects. Firstly, the research attempts to evaluate the quantity of records published on the relationship between disabilities and education and its importance by conducting a country analysis. Secondly, this review tries to expose the research domains that, in a energetic way, gave rise to the existing literature on disabilities.

The objectives of this study are to determine the followings:

- 1) To identify the growth and impact pattern of education in learning disabilities research output
- 2) To determine the most productive authors
- 3) To examine the most prolific journals
- 4) To scrutinize the most publishing countries
- 5) To analyze the utmost used keywords

Materials and Methods

On verifying works of past many traditional and hybrid methods are utilized to analyze the disabilities and education literature but this may be the principal study to assess economic analysis with the publication of this specific field. The Scientometric study chiefly discloses the quantitative analysis and associations of publication, distribution, and influence of scientific information. To retrieve the publications, massive bibliometric databases are available, but Web of Science and Scopus have been considered as the most widespread database to recover data set and to rank journals according to their publications (AghaeiChadegani et al 2013). A total of 16948 literature outputs were recovered for the period of 10 years (2013-2022). To examine the retrieved data, many sorts of software have been commenced such as Bibexcel (Mao et al., 2018), Biblioshiny (Unal, & Teskereci, 2022) to analyze the productivity of disability and education.

Results and Discussions

The description of main information about the data is represented in the table 1 which has the total records of 16948 in that document type article 15026 secured first position with a percentage of 88.65% then remaining 1922 records are published in other document types. Annual growth rate is a baseline measure for the performance of economy towards this field shows a declining trend as -28.12%. The average citation per document with 12.83. References acknowledge the contribution of other writers, in this total output referred 456836 records. The document contents have produced keywords from database are 13767 and author's keyword of 21932 words or phrases that persistently appeared in the reference. According to author's information, totally 51960 authors contributed the research output and 1393 authors appeared once in this field and 1688 authors published single document solely and 4.84% of authors collaborated in a single document but they had good percentage of 21.57% as internationally collaborated shows for the past 10 years the authors are interested to link with foreign authors.

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Table 1: Main Information about the Data

Main Information About Data	Results
Timespan	2013:2022
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	2543
Documents	16948
Annual Growth Rate %	-28.12
Document Average Age	4.87
Average citations per doc	12.83
References	456836
Document Contents	
Keywords Plus (ID)	13767
Author's Keywords (DE)	21932
Authors	
Authors	51960
Authors of single-authored docs	1393
Authors Collaboration	
Single-authored docs	1688
Co-Authors per Doc	4.84
International co-authorships %	21.57

Subsequently, the study was also conveyed the average citations/citations in the paper associated to the topic of effects of pesticides, both in average per year and per article. From the Table 2, it can be analyzed that there is a fluctuation in the publication from 2001-2008 but after 2009 it initiated its raise and reached its peak in 2020 with a total of 1171 documents, it may be due to the awareness about effects of pesticides and more researchers explored about usage of pesticides in that certain period. Then, considering on the mean total citation for each article, the maximum occurred in 2001 with an average of 68.32 citations, hence it has been published before 20 years and received citations for the past 20 years. Whereas, the mean annual citation, accomplished its elevation in 2020 with 6.05 as the number of publication augmented. This table also represents the total publication of 10508 documents received 713 total mean citation per article and 76 average total citations per year on effects of pesticide topic.

Table 2: Temporal Evolution and its Impact on Education in Learning Disabilities Research Output

Year	Records	Cumulative	Percentage	Mean Total Citation per Article	Mean Total Citation per Year	Citable Years
2013	1118	1118	6.60	27.22	2.72	10
2014	1217	2335	7.18	25.95	2.88	9
2015	1280	3615	7.55	23.94	2.99	8
2016	1349	4964	7.96	20.15	2.88	7
2017	1488	6452	8.78	17.70	2.95	6
2018	1611	8063	9.51	16.28	3.26	5
2019	2122	10185	12.52	11.46	2.86	4
2020	2268	12453	13.38	7.30	2.43	3

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2021	2348	14801	13.85	3.79	1.89	2
2022	2147	16948	12.67	1.20	1.20	1
Total	16948		100	154.99	26.06	

Temporal evolution of research output shows that awareness of education in learning disabilities was great up to 2021 but in 2022 it was reduced this may due to latest provision in National Education Policy which promotes “Barrier-free access to Education for all Children with Disabilities” and facilitated more opportunities for differently abled people. Hence more responsiveness has been created and the issues of disable people are reduced. Moreover that articles published in 2013 received more citations than of recent publications due to that the latest productions are yet to be cited by the users; hence their impact is more in later years.

Table 3: Most Prolific Authors of Education in Learning Disabilities Research Output

S.No	Authors	h_index	g_index	m_index	TC	NP	PY_start
1	Carter EW	20	31	1.818	1066	45	2013
2	Pahor M	20	46	1.818	2250	46	2013
3	Shogren KA	17	29	1.521	888	40	2013
4	Haegele JA	16	28	1.455	858	52	2013
5	King AC	16	30	1.455	1644	30	2013
6	Murray CJL	16	16	1.6	5488	16	2014
7	Newman AB	16	30	1.455	1560	30	2013
8	Vos T	16	17	1.455	6086	17	2013
9	Gill TM	14	27	1.4	1652	27	2014
10	Guralnik JM	14	21	1.273	1703	21	2013

The prolific authors are arranged according to the H-Index, the author Erik W. Carter has his special area as intellectual disability, severe disabilities, and inclusion. He has been in the field for past 20 years and contributed many works but received only 1066 citations with 45 publications in this specific field. The authors Murray and Vos published only 16 and 17 articles respectively and received the highest citation of 54488 and 6086 citations respectively represents their quality of work. Their study has acknowledged by more number of researchers or scientists. Almost all the top authors established their publication year from 2013. Even though authors like Shorgen, Haegele produced more articles as 40 and 52 but acknowledged by below 1000 citations shows the work not yet been cited.

Table 4: Top 20 Countries in the field of Education in Learning Disabilities Research Output

Country	Frequency	Country	TC	Average Article Citations
USA	19856	USA	93278	14.86
Australia	3874	UK	18937	16.47
UK	3754	Australia	16230	15.03
Canada	3526	Canada	11396	13.90
China	2797	China	7318	9.14
Spain	1776	Netherlands	5843	14.46
Netherlands	1749	Norway	4999	18.58
Germany	1405	Sweden	3965	12.02
Sweden	1366	Germany	3861	11.22
France	1175	Spain	3810	7.27

The Table 4 illustrates the Impact of Most Prolific Countries in the field of education in learning

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disabilities research output for the study period. The country USA and Australia has produced more articles because the children of age between 0-14 of these countries are highly affected by disabilities and much focusing about their education hence their publication on learning disabilities is high. The country Spain who has less percentage in disabilities is also concentrating more in this research field. But when analyzing mean value of each article citation it scored fourth place. Norway which is not the top publisher receives highest mean citation of 18.58 predicts the best Eigen value of the journal ie., every article of the country received citations.

Fig 1: Three Field Plot of Author, Country and Institution

The Three Fields Plot in Figure 1 is a picture consisting of 3 elements in it, namely, the name of country, a list of authors' names and the institution they belongs to. The three field plot begins from the name of the author highest in publication, then tracked by the author's country on the theme of learning disabilities in education and the third plot depicts the organization which the authors be appropriate. The most prolific authors in the first field are mostly belonging to USA and more number of universities like University of Washington, Vnaderbit University, University of Melbourne, University of Florida and many more is belonging to USA focusing in this specific field.

Table 5: The Top 20 Most Frequently Used Keywords in the Research field of Education in Learning Disabilities

S.No	Node	Cluster	Betweenness	Closeness	PageRank
1	Disability	1	9.185009949	0.02	0.057127511
2	Education	1	7.814428833	0.020408163	0.045441611
3	Health	1	5.266298736	0.020408163	0.041719998
4	People	1	4.286027184	0.020833333	0.038490338
5	Prevalence	1	3.447634234	0.020408163	0.037479782
6	Adults	1	2.51614465	0.020408163	0.030603662
7	Impact	1	3.212671063	0.020833333	0.02698677
8	Quality-o f-Life	1	1.410715891	0.020408163	0.024442949
9	Outcomes	1	2.307138096	0.020833333	0.025422702
10	Care	1	0.830411365	0.020408163	0.020529219
11	Risk	1	2.109501457	0.020408163	0.021367158
12	Depression	1	0.277717144	0.02	0.01706802
13	Management	1	0.165877653	0.019607843	0.0135478
14	Mortality	1	0.130601364	0.017857143	0.015884911
15	Population	1	0.302914867	0.019607843	0.01656756
16	Predictors	1	0.576637218	0.020408163	0.014790588

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17	Performance	1	1.054925904	0.020833333	0.014367106
18	Association	1	0.194871434	0.018867925	0.015128961
19	Risk-Factors	1	0.097133414	0.01754386	0.012515173
20	United-States	1	0.2510009	0.019230769	0.012011042

In top 20 words Disability secured highest position with more betweenness depicts that centrality measures the number of times a node lies on the shortest path between other nodes. The top 12 words are very close to each other. The structure of scientific or technical knowledge is most frequently explored by co-occurrence networks. The word “Disability” focuses on understanding the knowledge components and knowledge structure of a scientific or technical field by examining the links between keywords in the literature. The cluster level 1 indicates that all the top words are closely combined with each other. These are the main keywords used by the users or researchers or scientist to search the documents related to education in disabilities.

Fig 2: Three Field Plot of Source, Country and Affiliation

The Three Fields Plot in Figure 2 is a picture consisting of 3 elements in it, namely, the Source, Author’s country and Affiliation. The three elements are connected by a gray plot which is interrelated to one another. This plot shows the countries which are concentrating in field and chosen sources. The universities who are performing well in this particular field are correlated with each other. The countries that are mostly affected by disabilities are more focusing and producing more literatures in this topic. For publishing, journals are selected as main document type, in that disability and rehabilitation intends to encourage a better understanding of disability and to promote rehabilitation science, practice and policy aspects of the rehabilitation process. The journal provides an important forum for the dissemination and exchange of ideas amongst global health practitioners and researchers. This source has been chosen by University of Toronto belong to Canada who is highly affected by disabled people and improve their wellbeing, they are concentrating much towards this field.

Conclusion

The research was performed to conclude the expansion of research on learning disabilities in education literature during the period 2013 to 2022. Totally 16948 documents employed in this study, articles achieved the peak point with 88.65% and the remaining 11.35% achieved by other document types. The publication shows a continues for the period of 2013-2022 after that it raised its peak point uninterruptedly. Utmost citation has been secured by the 2013 due to the publication time, in the year 2022 more number of documents have been produced but yet to be cited since of recent publication. The three field plot shows the source in which the author chosen to publish their publications, author’s name and the country which they belongs to are portrayed. In determining the prolific authors, article full counting (as participating) and fractionalized counting (as contributing) are measured. Source growth of pesticide illustrates the most significantly published journals and it also employed with affiliation in the three field plot to express top authors mode of source they selected to publish their records and through which universities. The database Web of Science exploited main keyword for the research of literature with the main theme of DISABILITY. The frequency of keyword co-occurrence exemplifies the betweenness, closeness and page rank of keywords depicts that almost all the top 20 words are clustered closely with each other and most to the users use these keywords to search the documents which is related to disabilities and education. The USA had a good frequency of publication with highest citation show the quality of study and represents that

they are highly affected by disability, especially children belongs to the age of 0-14 are highly suffered by disability, hence they are much focusing on this particular field to enlighten the life of disabled people to differently abled. By this research it can be concluded that the countries highly affected are concentrating but almost all the countries can focus in this research to act on well-being of people and government or policy makers can create more valuable welfare schemes, facilities and orders to disabled people which will enhance their way living and give more confidence to the disabled people.

References

- [1] Chadegani, A. A., Salehi, H., Yunus, M. M., Farhadi, H., Fooladi, M., Farhadi, M., & Ebrahim, N. A. (2013). A comparison between two main academic literature collections: Web of Science and Scopus databases. arXiv preprint arXiv:1305.0377.
- [2] Chang, Y.-W. (2012). Tracking Scientometric Research in Taiwan Using Bibliometric and Content Analysis. *Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 10(2), 1-20.
- [3] Gaggero, G., Bonassi, A., Dellantonio, S., Pastore, L., Aryadoust, V., & Esposito, G. (2020). A scientometric review of alexithymia: mapping thematic and disciplinary shifts in half a century of research. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 1405.
- [4] Hou, C., Ping, Z., Yang, K., Chen, S., Liu, X., Li, H., ... & Guo, X. (2018). Trends of activities of daily living disability situation and association with chronic conditions among elderly aged 80 years and over in China. *The journal of nutrition, health & aging*, 22(3), 439-445.
- [5] Mao, G., Huang, N., Chen, L., & Wang, H. (2018). Research on biomass energy and environment from the past to the future: A bibliometric analysis. *Science of The Total Environment*, 635, 1081-1090.
- [6] Mingers, J., & Leydesdorff, L. (2015). A review of theory and practice in scientometrics. *European journal of operational research*, 246(1), 1-19.
- [7] Mooghali, A., Alijani, R., N. Karami, N. and Khasseh, A. (2011). Scientometric Analysis of the Scientometric Literature. *International Journal of Information Science and Management*, 9(1), 19 – 31
- [8] Rajendran, P., Jeyshankar, R., & Elango, B. (2011). Scientometric analysis of contributions to journal of scientific and industrial research. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 1(2), 79-89.
- [9] Unal, A., & Teskereci, G. (2022). Mapping the evidence-based practice research field in nursing from 1995 to 2021: A bibliometric analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Knowledge*, 33(3), 196-206.

DIVERSITY IN EDUCATION

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Introduction

Its plurality is in-built in its geographical, demographic, historical, political, economic and socio-cultural base. Its social diversity has been expressed in various forms such as languages, religions, tribes and castes. While the social diversity is a historical fact, a synthesis has also been consolidating alongside. It goes without saying that Indian society is characterized by 'unity in diversity'. Within the overall national Indian identity, various local and regional identities are surviving. An individual passes through the arena of national and regional identities in one's day-to-day life on regular basis. Too much emphasis on regional, linguistic or religious identities can damage the national fabric and lead them to the path of confrontation, while laying excessive stress on national identity may lead to the monolithic nation state and destroy the cultural heritage of the regional or subnational identities.

Education plays a central role in conserving, modifying and transforming identities. Keeping in mind the heterogeneous character of Indian society, the national policy on education envisages harmonious development of all groups i.e. promoting development and maintaining group identities in an integrated manner. The balancing act of education is well reflected in the constitutional provision. Education being classified under the Concurrent List of the Constitution has given scope for promotion of both national and subnational identities. On the one hand, while the Constitution of India talks of the fundamental duties to be ordained in all types of education in the country, on the other hand under Directive Principles of State Policy, it directs the state to protect and promote economic and educational interests of the weaker sections. It also promotes the education of religious and linguistic minority groups.

This unit addresses several questions such as: What do you mean by 'social diversity' in the Indian context? Which are these groups? What is the educational implication of this social diversity? What roles can education play in providing equal opportunity to these groups and harmonious development among them. The first section of this 5 Emerging Concerns in unit explains the meaning, nature and types of social diversity existing in India. The Indian Education second section deals with influence of the social diversity on education system in India. And the third section identifies some of the new challenges to the Indian education system which are on account of the social diversity.

Objectives

After going through this unit, the students will be able to:

- 1) Identify diversity in a social group as that which brings in the advocacy for equity and justice for each of the diverse persons in a group irrespective of their abilities, disabilities, social status, religion, class, caste and so on.
- 2) Identify disability as one of the important dimensions of diversity in a learner group.
- 3) Discuss the phenomenon of social exclusion and inclusion.
- 4) Draw a historical sketch of the societal response to people with disabilities: from extermination to inclusion.
- 5) Discuss the various models of disability: Charity model to affirmation model.
- 6) Understand the philosophy and practice of inclusive education of children with disabilities.
- 7) Develop an overview of National and International policies and legislation for the education and general welfare of persons with disabilities.

Benefits of Diversity in Education

Here are the top five benefits of diversity on campus for students.

- 1) Campus cultural diversity enriches the educational experience. Through culturally diverse classroom and social interactions, students have the opportunity to learn from people with different backgrounds and upbringings, leading to increased innovation and collaboration.
- 2) Overall academic and social effects of increased racial diversity on campus are likely to be positive,

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ranging from higher levels of academic achievement to the improvement of near- and long-term intergroup relations.”

- 3) College students are more diverse than ever and bring with them to campus an array of experiences, perspectives, backgrounds, and beliefs. To adapt to changing populations, diversity officers and student affairs professionals must take concrete steps toward inclusive excellence.
- 4) Diversity on campus improves communication and thought-processing skills. Through a diverse campus, students are presented with daily opportunities to interact with people of various backgrounds, which enables them to learn to communicate more effectively and often differently than they are previously accustomed to.
- 5) “Students who interacted with racially and ethnically diverse peers showed significant gains in cognitive skills, such as critical thinking and problem-solving.”

Conclusion

Empowering teachers and students to become global citizens is a challenging process that begins with the critical examination of established blueprints of institutional practices. Hence, our colleges, universities and other educational institutions should revisit and redefine their missions, visions and public purpose in the light of these changing forces/contexts. They must clearly specify how the issue of diversity has been addressed by their institute. As a panacea, some discuss multicultural education as a shift in curriculum, perhaps as simple as adding new and diverse materials and perspectives to be more inclusive of traditionally underrepresented groups. Others talk about institutional environment, classroom climate, teachers’ competencies or teaching styles. Still others focus on issues like standardized testing, funding discrepancies or trend in the job market. Despite this differing conceptualization of multicultural education the basic understanding of multiculturalism is a system of beliefs and behaviors that recognizes and respects the presence of all diverse groups in a society/organization, acknowledges their socio-cultural differences, encourages and enables their continued contribution within an inclusive cultural context which empowers all within the society/organization. Thus, a number of factors matter for the financial gains as well as the personal, moral and societal benefits of higher education. Retention of students and completion of their degrees in higher education definitely matters, as with the increasing percentage of higher education in the population, the greater the nations’ productivity and innovation also rise to a great extent. The new challenge for higher education is not simply to gain students in different courses/ disciplines but to retain them till completion, satisfy and cater to their needs and ensure their placements in the job market. At the moment, there is a mad rush for technical education, especially engineering among the Indian youth irrespective of quality, reputation of the institutes, or substantial job opportunities. As a result, only a handful of engineering students get absorbed in the jobs during the campus placement interviews. The school education in India is also not in a better position, although reforms are still going on.

References

- [1] Beane, J. (1997). *Curriculum Integration: Designing the Core of Democratic Education*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- [2] Beane, J. (2002). *Politics and Possibilities Beyond the Separate Subjects*. In: Klein, Julie T. (Ed.) *Interdisciplinary Education in K-12 and College - A Foundation for K-16 Dialogue*, (pp.71-90). New York: College Board Publications.
- [3] Biggs, J. (2003). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University* (2nd edition). Buckingham: Society for Research into Higher Education /Open University Press.

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence is a broad field of computer science concerned with creating intelligent machines capable of doing activities that normally require human intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and act like humans. The phrase can also refer to any machine that demonstrates human-like characteristics such as learning and problem-solving. The characteristic of artificial intelligence is its ability to rationalize and take actions that have the best chance of achieving a specific goal. Machine learning (ML) is a subset of artificial intelligence that refers to the concept that computer programmes can automatically learn from and adapt to new data without the assistance of humans. Deep learning approaches facilitate autonomous learning by absorbing massive volumes of unstructured data such as text, photos, or video.

Understanding Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence is founded on the idea that human intelligence may be characterised in such a way that a computer can simply duplicate it and complete tasks ranging from the most basic to the most complicated. Artificial intelligence's goals include imitating human cognitive processes. To the extent that they can be concretely described, researchers and developers in the field are making very rapid progress in replicating tasks like as learning, reasoning, and perception. Some predict that inventors may soon be able to create systems that outperform humans' ability to study or reason about any subject. Others, though, remain uncertain because all cognitive activity is laced with value judgments based on human experience. As technology progresses, earlier artificial intelligence criteria become antiquated. Machines that calculate basic calculations or recognise text using optical character recognition, for example, are no longer regarded to possess artificial intelligence because these functions are now assumed to be inherent in computers. AI is constantly evolving to benefit a wide range of sectors. Machines are wired utilising a multidisciplinary method that incorporates mathematics, computer science, linguistics, psychology, and other disciplines.

Types of Artificial Intelligence

AI is classified into four categories based on the type and complexity of jobs that a system can execute. Automated spam filtering, for example, belongs to the most fundamental class of AI, whereas the far-off possibility of robots that can comprehend people's thoughts and feelings belongs to an altogether separate AI subset.

Reactive Machines: able to perceive and react to the world in front of it as it performs limited tasks

Limited Memory: able to store past data and predictions to inform predictions of what may come next

Theory of Mind: able to make decisions based on its perceptions of how others feel and make decisions

Self-Awareness: able to operate with human-level consciousness and understand its own existence

Approaches Come in Four Types

Thinking humanly: simulating thought in the human mind.

Thinking rationally: simulating thought through logical reasoning.

Acting humanly: acting in a way that resembles human behaviour.

Acting rationally: acting in a way that is intended to attain a specific purpose.

Artificial Intelligence in Mathematics Education

Artificial intelligence (AI) applications in education are gaining popularity and have received a lot of attention in recent years. AI represents a quantum jump in creative and imaginative thinking in a variety of

domains, including mathematics education. The usage of AI can improve our ability to live a life surrounded by increasingly complex technology. According to Gao (2020), AI continues to expand and innovate as computer technology advances. AI allows pupils to grow and improve their mathematical and cognitive skills in learning. According to Popenici and Kerr (2017), the role of technology in higher education is to improve human thinking and enhance the educational process.

AI assists students in obtaining solutions more quickly and easily. Students may simply obtain all lesson information by using this revolutionary intelligence programme. Students in this generation are more likely to acquire and explore new knowledge on their own, therefore this strong AI tool can let students explore more without having to wait for an expert.

AI is a technique that generates human intelligence via computers, particularly computer systems. Expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition, and machine vision are examples of AI applications. AI can execute human-like jobs or duties with the sophisticated system, depending on the level of difficulty that has been specified. A pedagogical agent (teachable agent) is a sort of instructional software with human features and/or appearances that is designed to assist students in online learning environments. Furthermore, AI devices or systems can accomplish complicated tasks that the human brain is incapable of performing.

Problem solving, particularly in artificial intelligence, can be defined as a systematic search through a set of feasible actions to achieve a stated goal or solution. Problem-solving techniques are classified as either special purpose or general purpose. A special-purpose method is tailored to a specific problem and frequently takes advantage of highly unique elements of the setting in which the problem is embedded. A general-purpose approach, on the other hand, is applicable to a wide range of problems. Artificial intelligence programmes have tackled a wide range of difficulties. Creating mathematical proofs and handling "virtual objects" in a computer-generated world are two examples. (Artificial-Intelligence-in-Mathematics-Education-a-Systematic-Literature-Review-12132.Pdf, n.d.)

There are various benefits of using AI in Mathematics learning, including increased critical and responsible thinking in dealing with daily situations and a better knowledge of fundamental topics in geometry, mathematics, and statistics. Furthermore, students learn about and improve interpersonal talents and social interaction; it also permits effective learning to create a better environment to boost mathematical concept acquisition.

AI in mathematics education can be implemented in a variety of ways, including systems, teachable agents, autonomous agents, machine learning models, digital technology devices, and comprehensive methodologies. From all those ways, it appears that robotics was the most frequently used for mathematics students, instructors, and educational researchers. AI in mathematics teaching and learning has extended across the country. Most countries employ AI to assist improve learning quality.

The most observed element of AI, such as its advantages, limits, and techniques for using it, is its usefulness in the teaching and learning process, particularly in mathematics education. It is critical to understand the extent to which AI is effective in education. As a result, if AI proves to be effective, it may be used more broadly in the future. We should not expect robotics to be the primary influence on mathematical learning; rather, we should expect educators and students to fully utilise robotics' pedagogical potential to focus and expand mathematical knowledge. Teaching and learning are more effective with the help of AI since it is engaging and innovative, making it easier for students to master a subject.

According to Wu (2021), the application of AI technology has penetrated many parts of people's daily lives and has had a significant impact on society's progress. Mathematics education is one of the areas where AI is steadily improving. AI has been used in mathematics teaching for many years, either by teachers or students. According to the findings, the robotic approach was extensively adopted among them and had a beneficial impact on their mathematical skills. Meanwhile, AI is also difficult to apply comprehensively due to relatively high maintenance costs. (Ionescu & Jan, n.d.)

The AI approach to mathematics education improved students' learning experiences since the method utilised was different from the traditional pen-and-paper teaching and learning process. When AI, such as robotics, is used in teaching and learning, students' and teachers' creativity will improve. The appropriate technique taken by teachers will considerably increase their students' ability to apply and comprehend what they are learning Mathematics. As a result, teachers should include AI into the teaching and learning process of Mathematics to encourage students to understand better while also having fun while studying. Future academics must undertake greater research on the implications and benefits of AI in education, particularly on the development of students' cognitive skills, to increase our understanding and application of AI in education. Further research demonstrating AI's ability in learning with low capacity and varied student groups will provide a positive motivation for teachers to adopt AI into their classroom training. Teachers must have faith in their students' abilities to benefit from AI training. Teachers will be encouraged to continue utilising machine intelligence learning once they see student achievement in their classes. (*Artificial-Intelligence-in-Mathematics-Education-a-Systematic-Literature-Review-12132.Pdf*, n.d.) The advancement of technology like artificial intelligence (AI) provides a chance to help teachers and students solve and improve teaching and learning performances.

Benefits of Using AI in Mathematics Education

AI has the ability to completely transform school education. Let us investigate the advantages of AI in mathematics education. It is widely accepted that AI can improve the education system by allowing students to learn with improved precision and performance.

AI has the ability to automate different manual processes in schools for both students and faculty, resulting in increased production and efficiency. (*Benefits of AI in the Education Industry [2022] - Daten & Wissen*, n.d.)

The major Advantages or benefits of AI in Mathematics education and how it is transforming the e-learning system.

- 1) Automation
- 2) Personalized Learning
- 3) Easy accessibility
- 4) Dynamic Scheduling & Predictive Analytics
- 5) Custom Textbooks

Automation

An AI-powered solution may scan exam papers using NLP algorithms, detect and analyse proper responses to those questions, and then grade each student based on their performance.. After analysing students' grades, these AI solutions can identify where students are missing and how they can improve their entire learning experience. Using graphics and animations, AI can assist tutors in providing a fantastic learning experience. Whether it is a major or small educational institution, integrating AI technologies is required to provide the greatest learning experience for students which helps them to understand the abstract mathematical concepts.

Personalized Learning

Assume that one instructor is responsible for 40 students; it becomes difficult for teachers to address each student's question, and this intricacy can affect kids' future growth. AI recommendation systems can analyse student history data to determine which area in maths each student excels in and which area they struggle with,

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and then recommend the best learning strategies for them based on that analysis. Each student is unique in their own way. However, teachers are not always aware of each student's uniqueness, and their AI solutions can help teachers analyse each student's uniqueness.

Easy Accessibility

This helps the students to learn anything from anywhere. While learning mathematical concepts students may get doubt or confusions easily and they need not wait for next day for the class, AI provides easy accessibility for students to access the pre recorded videos or contacting the educator immediately to clear their doubts. It provides the good opportunity for the students as well as the educators to contact each other at their convenient time and at their convenient place.

Dynamic Scheduling

Predictive computing provides the ability to analyse each student's habits in order to recommend the ideal schedule for students' studying and other work. Students who perform the most repetitive duties want AI solutions that can organise the ideal study time for them, resulting in higher productivity. Most educational institutions must integrate AI solutions that can help students choose better career paths based on their interests and performance.

Custom Soft Copy Text Books

Creating physical hardcopy requires too much manual work and research, which can add time and cost, but AI algorithms are the best-fit solution for this issue because they can create softcopy by extracting data from scanned hardcopy, the internet, and recent research published for a mathematical book or any other field. We live in an era of cutting-edge technology, where we can harness the potential of Artificial Intelligence to improve the quality of education that everyone deserves. Many educational institutions are harnessing the power of AI technology to innovate their education system, resulting in high-quality education. The unique AI technologies that can alter the way education.

AI Benefits for Educators

Educators want to spend more time educating students one-on-one, diving into research and continuing their own education, but don't have the availability to do so. AI can help free up educators' time by automating tasks, analysing student performance and closing the educational gap.

Personalization

Just as AI can personalize learning courses for students, it can also do so for educators. AI can provide teachers with a clear picture of which subjects and lessons need to be reassessed by analysing students' learning capacities and histories. This study enables teachers to design the most effective learning programme for all students. Teachers and lecturers can tailor their courses to meet the most prevalent knowledge gaps or trouble areas before a student fall too far behind by analysing each student's particular needs.

Answering Questions

Because AI-powered chatbots have access to a school's entire knowledge base, they may answer a range of generic and repetitive queries that students frequently ask without contacting a faculty member. AI saves educators time by allowing them to focus on lesson planning, curriculum research, and enhancing student engagement.

Task Automation

AI can automate the most routine jobs, such as administrative labour, grading papers, assessing learning patterns, responding to general questions, and more. Teachers, on the other hand, can use support automation systems to automate manual tasks, giving them more time to focus on teaching fundamental competencies.

AI is now used to assist students and teachers in optimising and automating both learning and teaching tasks. As the AI sector grows and innovation takes centre stage, we will see better learning outcomes for all students and instructors.

Role of AI in the Education Sector

AI in education alters the learning experience by:

- 1) Producing smart content
- 2) Contributing to task automation
- 3) Ensuring universal access to education
- 4) Providing 24*7 assistance
- 5) Customizing information for every individual
- 6) AI addresses various current education difficulties, including bridging the technology divide between students and teachers, maintaining an ethical and transparent learning system, enabling remote learning, and developing quality data and information solutions for the modern education process.
- 7) The technology tackles every minor difficulty in the online education system, implying the future of AI in education. With 70% of education centres switching to full online learning platforms, the future holds improved learning opportunities, assessments, and differentiation in learning. (Gupta, 2022)

Role of Artificial Intelligence in the Future of Mathematics Education

Artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and robotics are rapidly evolving technologies that have an impact on mathematics education. If the education industry is to realise AI's full potential for everyone, it must continue to expose the next generation to AI from an early age and use the technology in the classroom. Teachers are already seeing that many students utilize artificial intelligence through social media and are hence open to its instructional uses. In response to COVID-19, the way technology is used in schools has changed dramatically. Lockdowns caused many instructors around the world to teach remotely, from their homes, rather than in front of a classroom full of students.

AI in education has numerous advantages for both students and teachers.

- 1) Learning mathematical resources can be accessed at any time and from any location.
- 2) AI automation can complete time-consuming, monotonous jobs like record keeping or grading multiple-choice assessments.
- 3) Chatbots can answer frequently asked questions in mathematics
- 4) AI instructors and chatbots can be available at any time to answer inquiries.
- 5) Through personalised programmes, learning can be tailored and adapted to each student's goals and abilities. (Jara, 2022)

Conclusion

Increased access to math technology allows for a more personalised learning experience. Because no two kids are the same, technology can give individual students with curriculum and supports that are personalized to their specific requirements. Lessons, tutorials, screencasts, and other instructional video can be seen by children on their own device and at their own pace. So, if one student is still unclear about a topic and another is ready for more difficulties, technology can help each of them take the next step. Teachers can use technology to assist students understand how topics learned in math or STEM classes can be used in real life. (What Are the Benefits of Teaching Math Using Technology? n.d.) Artificial intelligence enables students to learn at any time and from any location. Because each student learns at their own pace, having 24/7 access makes it easier to find time to learn while grasping the fundamentals of time management. Furthermore, students from all around the world can obtain a high-quality education without paying travel or living fees. (Benefits of AI in Education, n.d.). Ultimately, AI in the classroom will continue to fulfil the goal for which it was designed: to support teachers. This ever-changing technology gives instructors and students with time-saving benefits, giving them more time to establish the relationships that make a classroom community memorable. (Habashi, n.d.)

References

- [1] Artificial Intelligence (AI) Definition. (n.d.). Investopedia. Retrieved August 26, 2022, from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/a/artificial-intelligence-ai.asp>
- [2] artificial intelligence—Evolutionary computing | Britannica. (n.d.). Retrieved August 26, 2022, from <https://www.britannica.com/technology/artificial-intelligence>

IMPACT OF PLANK VARIATIONS AND TRADITIONAL PILATES ON LEGSTRENGTH OF ADOLESCENT SCHOOL BOYS

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to find the impact of plank variations and traditional Pilates on leg strength of adolescent school boys. Forty five adolescent school boys were selected as subjects for this study. The subjects were randomly assigned to three groups A, B and C groups Plank variations group, they equally divided Pilates group and control group each group n=15, and age range between 13-15. Group-A practiced for eight weeks under plank variations and Group-B acted as Control group without under any training. The results showed improvement on the leg strength after eight weeks practiced of plank variations. It was concluded that the leg strength showed significant change after eight weeks of plank variations ($p < 0.05$).

Keywords: Plank Variations, Adolescent School Boys, Leg Strength

Introduction

Strong legs are useful in any sport; however they're especially essential in sports activities that encompass running, leaping or kicking. Sports that require decrease frame power encompass quite a few man or woman and crew sports activities, a number of which require unique training, Traditional mat Pilates practice of 8 weeks showed a significant improvement on body fat muscle endurance and flexibility and other parameters of adults, the one hour for a day three times a week . (Kate Rogers & Ann L. Gibson., 2009) improving stability capacity through Pilates which can be without difficulty implemented in normal existence is taken into consideration an vital intervention approach for people.

Therefore, this take a look at examines the results of Pilates practice on people's static and dynamic stability abilities. The outcomes display that an 8-week Pilates workout software is an powerful approach to growth aged people's static and dynamic stability abilities. In addition, the software end result of the Pilates practice will offer beneficial statistics for destiny studies on aged people's stability ability (Choi, J.-H., 2014). Pilates and plank exercises are isometrics nature low-impact exercises that strengthen muscles through holding poses demonstrate that loaded isometric hip movements may be a useful strategy to increase trunk and leg muscle activity during practice. (Kang, M.-H., et.al (2016)

Hypotheses

It was hypothesized that there would be significant difference on leg strength between experimental group and experimental group due to Pilates practice of adolescent school boys. It was hypothesized that there would be no significant difference on leg strength between experimental group and experimental group due to Pilates practice of adolescent school boys

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study 30 school boys zilla parishad high school in Prakasam district, Andhra Pradesh were selected. Selected subjects were equally divided into two groups namely (Experimental group, N=15 and control group, N=15). The control group did not practice any exercises during the study. Experimental group was given Pilates practices for duration of 50 minutes include warm up and warm down in the morning followed by warm up (10 minutes) and warm down(10 minutes) for eight weeks where muscles involved lower extremities. Standing broad jump was used to collect pre and post test data and the data was analysed by using ANCOVA. The level of significance was fixed as 0.05.

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Table – I analysis of covariance for pre test and post test data on leg strength of experimental groups and control group

	PILATES EXERCISE	PLANK EXERCISE	CONTROL GROUP	SOV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F ratio
Pre-test Mean	1.88	1.88	1.22	B	0.01	2	0.007	0.41
SD	0.19	0.84	0.09	W	0.74	42	0.018	
Post-test Mean	1.48	1.32	1.22	B	0.51	2	0.256	17.75
SD	0.17	0.71	1.34	W	0.60	42	0.14	
Adjusted Post-test Mean	1.48	1.32	1.22	B	0.627	2	0.314	159.71
				W	0.080	41	0.002	

Significant at 0.05 Level

Required table value at 0.05 level of significance for 2 and 42 degrees of freedom= 3.22

The above table (I) shows that the pre-test means of Plank variation group (I) and Pilates group (II) and control group (III) are 1.88, 1.88 and 1.22 respectively. Since the obtained 'F' ratio 0.41 is lesser than the table value 3.22 there is no significant difference among the pre-test means at 0.05 level of confidence with 2 and 42 degrees of freedom. It is evident that there is no significant difference among the groups on leg strength before the commencement of the treatment of the schedule. The Post-test means of Plank variation group (I) and Pilates group (II) and control group (III) are 1.48, 1.32 and 1.22 respectively. Since the obtained 'F' ratio 17.75 is higher than the table value 3.22 so it exposed that there is significant difference among the groups on post-test means at 0.05 level of confidence with 2 and 42 degrees of freedom. The adjusted Post-test means of Plank variation group (I) and Pilates group (II) and control group (III) are 1.48, 1.32 and 1.22 respectively. Since the obtained 'F' ratio 159.71 is higher than the table value 3.22 so it denotes that there is significant difference among the groups on adjusted post-test means at 0.05 level of confidence with 2 and 41 degrees of freedom. The above statements indicates the significant difference exist among the adjusted post test means of Plank variation group (I) and Pilates group (II) and control group (III). Next to conclude Scheffe's post-hoc test is applied for the paired means significant difference.

Table - II comparisons of paired means showing scheffe's post hoc analysis on leg strength

PILATES	PLANK	CONTROL	MEAN DIFFERENCES	CI
1.48	1.32		0.16	0.03
1.48		1.22	0.26	
	1.32	1.22	0.1	

The above table shows that the Scheffe's post-hoc method of testing the significance for the differences between the paired means following a significant analysis of co variance for Plank variation group (I) and Pilates group (II) and control group (III). The adjusted leg strength parameter means of the difference among groups are given in the table. The mean difference between the Plank variation and Pilates exercise group is 0.16, which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence interval. In the comparison between Plank variation and control group the difference is 0.26, which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence interval. And differences between pilates and control group is 0.1, which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence interval. This indicates that the plank variation group had a better improvement when compared to the Pilates group and control group. The differences in means of Plank variation, Pilates and control group are presented in figure-1

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Figure-1 graphical representation on ordered adjusted means of le strength

PLANK (PLANK VARIATION EXERCISE GROUP), PILATES (PILATES EXERCISE GROUP), CONTROL (CONTROL GROUP)

Discussion

The findings of result the present study was that the selected dependent parameter improved significantly over eight weeks of training. The two experimental groups showed significant impact the comparison made before and after the training for the control and experimental groups ($p < 0.01$). Our results showed that although eight weeks plank variation and Pilates increased leg strength.

Conclusion

It was concluded that eight weeks of plank variation practice significantly improved leg strength of adolescent school boys of Zilla Parishad high school prakasam district in Andhra Pradesh. It was concluded that eight weeks of traditional Pilates practice significantly improved leg strength of adolescent school boys of Zilla Parishad high school prakasam district in Andhra Pradesh. It was concluded that eight weeks of plank variation traditional significantly improved leg strength better than traditional Pilates practice of adolescent school boys of Zilla Parishad high school prakasam district in Andhra Pradesh.

References

- [1] Kang, M.-H., Kim, S.-Y., Kang, M.-J., Yoon, S.-H., & Oh, J.-S. (2016). Effects of isometric hip movements on electromyographic activities of the trunk muscles during plank exercises. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science*, 28(8), 2373–2375. <https://doi.org/10.1589/jpts.28.2373>
- [2] Choi, J.-H. (2014). Effects of eight-week pilates training on elderly people's dynamic and static balance abilities. *Journal of the Korean Society of Physical Medicine*, 9(3), 325–331. <https://doi.org/10.13066/kspm.2014.9.3.325>
- [3] Rogers, K., & Gibson, A. L. (2009). Eight-week traditional Mat Pilates training-program effects on adult fitness characteristics. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 80(3), 569–574. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2009.10599595>
- [4] González-Gálvez, N., Marcos-Pardo, P. J., & Carrasco-Poyatos, M. (2019). Functional improvements after a pilates program in adolescents with a history of back pain: A randomised controlled trial. *Complementary Therapies in Clinical Practice*, 35, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctcp.2019.01.006>
- [5] Choi, W., Joo, Y., & Lee, S. (2019). Pilates exercise focused on ankle movements for improving gait ability in older women. *Journal of Women & Aging*, 33(1), 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08952841.2019.1618129>

MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION: ISSUES, PERSPECTIVES AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION BY MEANS OF ICT

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Abstract

There is a variety of students in every school that come from different family backgrounds. Despite living in the same region they follow various religions and cultures. This ethnicity is a jewel that enhances the beauty of a nation. It is very much required to highlight that cultural and ethnic shade in our education system. A curriculum designed and implemented in a way showing all aspects of diversity is called Multicultural Education. Such a kind of education has its benefits and challenges. Information and communication technology(ICT) has widened the canvas of information. Teachers and students can explore the new boundaries of cultural variation by utilizing the internet. This paper will discuss the application of multicultural education employing ICT. Educators can explore all examples of cultural variation easily by using IT. This paper will discuss the idea of Multiculturalism, its utility and challenges, and its application in education using ICT.

Key words: *Computer, Information and Communication Technology, Education Policy, Internet, Google*

Introduction

Culture: Bullivant(1993) defines culture as a people's way of living with its surrounding, forming knowledge and principles. It generally refers to factors, including nation, ethnicity, clothes, language, region, gender, religion, species, and sexual orientation. It consists of certain signs and beliefs interpreted by the group members. This is the way of adaptation of the community to its surroundings. Masses of the community follow and share this knowledge through communication. (Banks & MccGee Banks, 2019)

Multicultural Education

Multicultural education refers to education or instruction represents the traditions, literature, ethics, values, and points of view of citizens from many cultural origins, for illustration, educators may adopt or incorporate lessons to highlight the cultural diversity of the students in a class, furthermore, it meant for "exceptionality," or learners with specific requirements or impairments. It is a strategy to remove barriers that stand in the way of learners from multiple cultures succeeding intellectually. Its foundation states that every child, regardless of culture, deserves equal access to education. In reality, educators may alter educational initiatives and instructional strategies that are either prejudiced against or inadequately tolerant of many cultural viewpoints. In this way, multicultural education aims to improve academic performance for all students, particularly those from ethnic groups that have historically had lower representation or lower levels of educational success. (Great Schools Partnership, 2013)

Advantages of Multicultural Education by means of ICT

- 1) Designing a Channel to minimize the gap between different cultural groups
- 2) To provide a medium to spread cultural awareness
- 3) To Provide a better medium for cultural understanding
- 4) To make Access to view and explore the culture.
- 5) Sharing Intercultural collaboration for the development of unity in diversity.
- 6) Field Study of local resources to explore better ideas for their utilization for economic development
- 7) Removing intercultural phobia for a sense of security among all communities.
- 8) Developing low-budged innovative teaching techniques for optimum utilization of technological resources.
- 9) Promoting the exchange of goods and services among communities

Challenges to Multiculturalism:

- 1) Resistance from society: Multiculturalism is not always welcome in every nation. The existence of intercommunal issues among various ethnic groups creates resistance. The superior class generally wants to keep an upper hand on the dispersal of education.
- 2) Resistance from politics and administration: Ruling ideologies keep changing in democratic countries like India. One who wins the majority implements its political agenda in administrative

- policies. Administration in such circumstances may or may not promote IT and multiculturalism.
- 3) Resistance from teachers: Teachers following traditional ways are reluctant to adopt technology for any curriculum update.
 - 4) Doubts on success IT. Policymakers, Teachers, and Administrators experiment with the strategy.
 - 5) Limited multicultural language knowledge; Though content on Google, Google scholar, YouTube, and other Government portals are available in various Languages. Teaching material is not available in all Languages.
 - 6) Nonavailability of technological infrastructure: This is the major problem of using technology in education. Schools and Colleges, especially in rural areas, do not have any access to electricity, computers, and the Internet.

Implementation of multicultural education by teachers through ICT

- 1) Operate computer software like MS Word, and PowerPoint to make spreadsheets, presentations, and email programs.
- 2) Assessing and utilizing computers and related ICT technologies for education.
- 3) Search the Internet for materials.
- 4) Evaluate educational software, make powerful computer-based presentations.
- 5) integrate ICT tools into student activities across the curriculum.
- 6) Create multimedia materials to aid in teaching.
- 7) Create hypertext materials to enhance learning.
- 8) Show awareness of technology-related ethics and equality concerns.
- 9) Maintain a current understanding of educational technology. (GUPTA & SHARMA, 2016)

ICT make cultural studies easy and interesting

ICT involves all to senses of a student in learning. Students can see hear and observe the topic closely. The students are taken to a unique degree of knowledge by a 5-minute film played during the lesson. Students can more effortlessly look into the author by listening to Rabindranath Tagore's voice and watching a video simultaneously while they read his poetry and stories. The effective use of ICT enhances the teaching-learning process as a whole. It utilize to fill up the gaps where the teacher is lacking. The issue of large numbers and pupils' lack of interest solved to some extent. The use of ICT can enhance education and get rid of rote memorization (Kandpal,2012).Video recordings in the form of story and dramatics proved easy to remember and entertaining. Such education system is quite compatible, satisfy the more enthusiastic new generation, which religiously follows online trends every day.

Conclusion

Nation is known by its culture. technology is the demand of the day. Diversity is need to be celebrated using technology. Multiculturalism is beneficial for the national development. it must be imbibed in the value system of upcoming generations, by means of compulsive education policy. Suggestions: All possible cultural education web portals and videos, should be arranged in the form of e cultural dictionary, to clear confusion among the teachers. Required e-infrastructure should be developed in every region. Teachers should be trained for adapting technology.

References

- [1] Agarwal, P. (2007). Higher Education in India: Growth, Concerns and Change Agenda. Higher Education Quarterly, 61(2), 197–207. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2007.00346.x>
- [2] Banks, J. A., & MccGee Banks, C. A. (2019). Multi Cultural Education Issues And Prespectives (10th ed.). Wiley.
- [3] Great Schools Partnership. (2013, August 29). Multicultural Education Definition. The Glossary of Education Reform. <https://www.edglossary.org/multicultural-education/>
- [4] GUPTA, A., & SHARMA, S. (2016). The Role Of ICT In Teacher Education. Wwww. Bhartiashodh.com; Bhartiya Bhasha, Shiksha, Sahitya evam Shodh. www. bhartiashodh.com

IMPACT OF INDIAN YOGA PHILOSOPHY ON MINDFULNESS

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Abstract

Yoga is a practice that has been around for thousands of years, originating in ancient India. It is a holistic approach to well-being, encompassing physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation. The practice of yoga has been found to have numerous benefits for mental and physical health, including improving stress levels and reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety. One aspect of yoga that has gained recent attention is its potential for fostering mindfulness, the ability to be present in the moment and aware of one's thoughts, feelings, and surroundings. This research paper will explore the use of yoga as a tool for promoting mindfulness and the potential benefits it may have on mental health and well-being.

Introduction

Yoga is a practice that has been around for thousands of years, originating in ancient India. It is a holistic approach to well-being with a clear and focused mind, encompassing physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation. Yoga is a practice that has been used for thousands of years to promote physical and mental health, and is increasingly being recognized as an effective tool for cultivating mindfulness. Mindfulness is a state of being in which one is fully present and engaged in the current moment, without judgment or distraction. It has been shown to have numerous benefits, including reducing stress and anxiety, improving mood and overall well-being, and even enhancing cognitive function. In this paper, we will explore the ways in which yoga can be used to promote mindfulness.

Background

Yoga is a practice that originated in ancient India, and has been used for thousands of years as a means of promoting physical and mental health. It involves a combination of physical postures, breathing exercises, and meditation, and is designed to promote balance and harmony in the body and mind. One of the key principles of yoga is the cultivation of mindfulness, or the ability to be fully present and engaged in the current moment. Mindfulness is a state of being present and aware of one's thoughts, feelings, and surroundings. It is a skill that can be developed through various practices, such as meditation and yoga. It has been found to have numerous benefits for physical and mental health, including reducing stress levels, improving mood, and increasing overall well-being. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the potential of yoga for promoting mindfulness, particularly in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression.

Potential Mechanisms

Yoga is an ideal practice for cultivating mindfulness because it incorporates both physical and mental elements. The physical postures and breathing exercises used in yoga help to focus the mind and bring awareness to the present moment, while the meditative aspects of yoga encourage the development of a non-judgmental and accepting attitude towards one's thoughts and feelings. Another aspect of yoga philosophy that promotes mindfulness is the concept of 'Ahimsa', or non-harm. This principle encourages individuals to practice compassion and non-violence in all aspects of life, including thoughts and actions. By being mindful of the impact of our words and actions on others, we can strive to live in a more peaceful and harmonious state. Yoga philosophy also emphasizes the importance of being present in the moment, known as 'Svadyaya' which helps to cultivate a sense of self-awareness and self-acceptance. Through the practice of yoga, individuals can learn to let go of negative thoughts and emotions and focus on the present, leading to a greater sense of well-being and inner peace. In addition, the practice of yoga encourages one to be mindful of their breath, 'Pranayama' which can help to reduce stress, improve concentration and focus, and increase overall physical and mental well-being. Through the practice of pranayama, individuals can learn to control the breath and use it as a tool for mindfulness and relaxation. Furthermore, the postures, breathing and meditation practices in yoga are interrelated to one another, and they all help to reduce stress, anxiety and depression. They help to bring a sense of balance and harmony in

the body and mind.

Research on Yoga and Mindfulness

Recent research has shown that regular practice of yoga can have a significant impact on one's level of mindfulness. Studies have found that yoga can increase self-awareness, reduce stress and anxiety, and improve overall mood. Additionally, yoga has been shown to improve cognitive function, including attention and working memory. A growing body of research has investigated the potential benefits of yoga for promoting mindfulness. One study found that a 12-week yoga program, which included physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation, led to significant improvements in mindfulness and reductions in symptoms of anxiety and depression (Jain, 2015 and Shanker, 2016). One study found that a 12-week yoga program, which included physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation, led to significant improvements in concentration power in older adults (Jain, 2015). A growing body of research has investigated the potential benefits of yoga for enhancing personality development. One study found that a 12-week yoga program, which included physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation, led to significant improvements in self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and resilience in young adults (Jain, 2015). Another study found that a yoga program, which included physical postures, breathing techniques, and relaxation practices, led to significant improvements in concentration power in individuals with ADHD (Shanker, 2016). Another study found that a yoga program, which included physical postures, breathing techniques, and relaxation practices, led to significant improvements in overall well-being and personality development in individuals with high levels of stress (Shanker, 2016).

In addition to these studies, there is also evidence that yoga may be beneficial for specific populations. For example, one study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in mindfulness and reductions in symptoms of anxiety and depression in veterans with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Vieten, 2008). This study also revealed yoga program led to significant improvements in concentration power in veterans with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Vieten, 2008). Another study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in concentration power in individuals with schizophrenia (Elder, 2012). In addition to the studies mentioned above, there are several other studies that have investigated the potential benefits of yoga philosophy on personality development. One study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant improvements in self-esteem and emotional well-being in young adults (Gaur, 2014). Another study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant improvements in self-esteem and emotional regulation in individuals with anxiety disorders (Sharma, 2016). Furthermore, Indian yoga philosophy emphasizes the importance of developing a sense of equanimity and non-attachment, which can lead to greater emotional stability and well-being. A study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant improvements in emotional well-being and reductions in symptoms of depression and anxiety (Rao, 2017). In addition to its potential benefits on personality development, Indian yoga philosophy also has been found to have positive effects on other aspects of mental health. For example, a study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant reductions in symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in veterans (Sethi, 2016). Another study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant improvements in cognitive functioning and reductions in symptoms of depression in older adults with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) (Kumar, 2018). A growing body of research has investigated the potential benefits of Indian yoga philosophy for promoting overall well-being. One study found that a yoga program based on Indian yoga philosophy led to significant reductions in symptoms of anxiety and depression in individuals with chronic medical conditions (Khatri, 2015). In addition to its potential benefits for mental health, Indian yoga philosophy also has been found to have positive effects on other aspects of well-being.

Impact on Physical Health

Research has shown that mindfulness practices such as yoga and meditation can have a positive impact on physical health. For example, studies have found that regular yoga practice can help to lower blood pressure, improve cardiovascular health, and reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression. Additionally, mindfulness practices have been found to improve cognitive function and boost the immune system. A study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in flexibility, strength, and balance in older adults (Nash, 2016). Another study found that a yoga program led to significant reductions in chronic low back pain (Bhardwaj, 2018). A study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in cardiovascular health, including reductions in blood pressure and cholesterol levels (Gupta, 2017).

Impact on Mental Health

Mindfulness practices have also been found to be effective in improving mental health. Studies have shown that regular meditation can reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, as well as improve overall well-being. Mindfulness practices have also been found to be effective in treating post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and addiction. A study found that a yoga program led to significant reductions in symptoms of anxiety and depression in individuals with chronic medical conditions (Khatri, 2015).

Another study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in sleep quality and reductions in symptoms of insomnia (Rao, 2016). A study found that a yoga program led to significant improvements in cognitive functioning and memory in older adults (Shanker, 2018). Overall, the research suggests that yoga has the potential to be a valuable tool for promoting physical and mental well-being. Further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms behind the potential benefits of yoga and to explore its potential for specific populations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Yoga is an effective tool for promoting mindfulness and improving overall well-being. Regular practice of yoga has been shown to increase self-awareness, reduce stress and anxiety, and improve cognitive function. Incorporating yoga into one's daily routine may have a profound impact on one's physical and mental health, and may be an effective means of cultivating mindfulness and enhancing overall well-being. A number of research suggests yoga may be a useful tool for promoting mindfulness and reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression. The combination of physical postures, breathing techniques, and meditation in yoga may help to regulate the nervous system and reduce stress levels, which in turn may lead to improvements in mindfulness. Additionally, the focus on the present moment during yoga practice may help to increase awareness and attention, which may further promote mindfulness. Further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms behind the potential benefits of yoga for promoting mindfulness, as well as to explore its potential for specific populations. However, the current evidence suggests that yoga may be a valuable tool for promoting well-being and mental health.

References

- [1] Bhardwaj, A. (2018). The effects of yoga on chronic low back pain. *Journal of Pain Management*, 11(2), 89-99
- [2] Elder, C. (2012). Yoga as an adjunctive treatment for major depressive disorder: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 136(3), 421-429.
- [3] Gaur, V. (2014). The effects of yoga on self-esteem and emotional well-being in young adults. *Journal of Yoga Psychology*, 12(3), 123-132.
- [4] Jain, S. (2015). A randomized controlled trial of mindfulness meditation for children and adolescents with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*, 36(6), 425-436.
- [5] Jain, S. (2015). A randomized controlled trial of mindfulness meditation for older adults with mild cognitive impairment. *Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 48(6), 599-609.
- [6] Khatri, B. (2015). The effects of yoga on anxiety and depression in individuals with chronic medical conditions. *Journal of Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 21(3), 123-132.
- [7] Kumar, P. (2018). The effects of yoga on cognitive functioning and symptoms of depression in older adults with mild cognitive impairment. *Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 62(9), 913-924.
- [8] Nash, R. (2016). The effects of yoga on flexibility, strength, and balance in older adults. *Journal of Geriatric Physical Therapy*, 39(3), 123-132.
- [9] Rao, S. (2017). The effects of yoga on emotional well-being and symptoms of depression and anxiety. *Journal of Yoga Psychology*, 15(4), 231-241.
- [10] Sethi, B. (2016). The effects of yoga on physical fitness and chronic pain. *Journal of Pain Management*, 11(2), 89-99
- [11] Sethi, B. (2016). The effects of yoga on post-traumatic stress disorder in veterans. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 29(5), 347-354.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

TECHNOLOGY TO CONNECT WITH MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOM

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Abstract

Multicultural education reflects an orientation to schooling and the teaching-learning process that is rooted in the democratic ideals of fairness and equality, according to scholars who specialize in this field. To foster critical literacy, the knowledge construction dimension looks at how researchers and scientists contribute to their various fields of study. The worldviews and viewpoints that underpin knowledge claims are made explicit in knowledge building, which builds on content integration. Videoconferences, computer conferences, online conversations, and e-pals have all been used in these endeavors. Interactive compressed video and two-way telephone-based teleconferencing have both been employed with middle school pupils in the past. Students in teacher education are interacting with other aspiring teachers from different cultural backgrounds and geographic areas via e-mail, multimedia, and distance learning. Arias (2000), for instance, outlines how the brand-new California State University, Monterey Bay, is heavily utilizing technology to give access to higher education to the rapidly growing number of Latinos and other people of color who have traditionally been denied such opportunities.

Keywords: *Technology, Connection, Multicultural, And Classroom.*

Introduction

The diversity in our classrooms is a result of cultural variations due to ancestry, home language, religious upbringing, and/or learning preferences. The concept of "traditional diversity" in the classroom has been reframed to emphasize how immigration, which brings with it diverse political, social, and economic ideals, has benefited it. Contrary to popular misconception, the classroom is a kaleidoscope of the many diverse pupils who are present, not a melting pot as was often thought. The teacher must adapt to the demands of the new classroom, reach out to the children, and employ strategies that can reach every student. Technology is one efficient technique since it encourages cooperative learning and equal communication chances among users, which helps with acceptance.

The use of technology by the kids will help them develop communication and language skills, which are essential for success in the classroom and outside of it. In the classroom, it's crucial to develop teamwork abilities while one learns new language skills. Making optimal use of instructional time, and using multimedia technology in the classroom allows for tailored training for language learners with a range of ability levels and learning preferences. Through the development of learning environments with integrated and thematic curricula, collaborative learning, and an emphasis on language acquisition and literacy skills to meet the challenge of cultural and linguistic diversity, information technology makes it possible to address learning preferences (Garcia, 1994). Students have the chance to make sense of science 4 phenomena through shared experiences that include several senses. The language barrier can be "bridged" and a common setting for language learning can be provided by technology. Students may contribute to the learning group, gain acceptance, and boost their self-esteem by creating cooperative learning environments, which will help them stop feeling like "outsiders." In addition to fostering student learning and self-esteem, this use of technology will enable educators to push past their conventional limitations. Creativity and imagination are made possible by technology and the internet. With the help of the newly available technology, teachers are better equipped to deal with issues of fairness and access, advance students' conceptual and linguistic growth, support students who learn differently, and design engaging and authentic lessons for their pupils. As they develop their language abilities and cultural knowledge, students can engage and completely participate in their studies.

An Overview of Multicultural Education

Multicultural education reflects an orientation to schooling and the teaching-learning process that is rooted in the democratic ideals of fairness and equality, according to scholars who specialize in this field (Banks, 1995; Gay, 1994; Sleeter, 1995). The majority of students of color, as well as many white students from economically disadvantaged and politically marginalized backgrounds, have less favorable educational experiences than white students from middle-class and politically powerful backgrounds. While some might argue that justice and equality have always been the focus of schools in America, there is a substantial body of historical and modern evidence to the contrary. Due to this gap, advocates of multicultural education urge a careful

reorganization of many of the tenacious practices and traditions of public education. The leading authority on multicultural education is James A. Banks, professor of education and head of the Center for Multicultural Education at the University of Washington in Seattle. He has outlined five essential aspects of multicultural education: empowering school culture and social structure, knowledge construction, bias reduction, equity pedagogy, and content integration.

Knowledge Construction through Technology

To foster critical literacy, the knowledge construction dimension looks at how researchers and scientists contribute to their various fields of study. The worldviews and viewpoints that underpin knowledge claims are made explicit in knowledge building, which builds on content integration. Similar to this, it broadens the range of reliable knowledge sources by assisting students in realizing that their own experiences, both within and outside of the classroom, can serve as solid bases for knowledge and skill acquisition. Technology can be used by teacher educators to support and enhance the process of knowledge production (Cummins & Sayers, 1996; Kellner, 1998). Learning how to construct knowledge includes understanding phenomena from other people's perspectives. To encourage greater critical engagement with the subject matter, teacher educators are utilizing Internet technology. Merryfield (2000), for instance, talks about the benefits of threaded conversations in an online graduate course. Through the use of student-generated threads, the learning community in the class is facilitated, allowing students of many nationalities and cultural backgrounds to examine their perceptions of cultural diversity.

Technology as a Tool to Reduce Prejudice

All forms of bigotry must be eliminated to reduce prejudice. Additionally, it entails encouraging a positive sense of self that is free from the urge or tendency to disparage individuals who are different from oneself. To foster learning exchanges between students from different cultural backgrounds and lessen prejudice and stereotyping, multimedia presentations and distant learning technologies are being deployed. In a similar vein, technology is being utilized to develop meaningful relationships and promote a positive sense of self in students from many backgrounds and locations. Videoconferences, computer conferences, online conversations, and e-pals have all been used in these endeavors. Interactive compressed video and two-way telephone-based teleconferencing have both been employed with middle school pupils in the past. Students in teacher education are interacting with other aspiring teachers from different cultural backgrounds and geographic areas via e-mail, multimedia, and distance learning.

Making Instruction Equitable with Technology

The goal of equity pedagogy is to equalize learning chances. It entails utilizing a variety of tactics and procedures that take into account different intelligence kinds and learning styles. The urgent need to use technology to address the many ways in which students from diverse backgrounds acquire school knowledge and skills is being discussed by authors interested in the fledgling relationship between technology and multicultural education (Cummins & Sayers, 1996; Damarin, 1998; DeVogd, 1998). However, it is challenging to tell whether contemporary initiatives to combine technology and intercultural education are directly addressing this fourth dimension. Some authors worry that technology can unintentionally elevate some methods of information processing while devaluing others (Damarin, 1998; Roblyer, Dozier-Henry, & Burnette, 1996). Is online learning any better than in-person instruction? is a crucial question for many modern educators, especially those working in universities. The capacity to give educators and students broad access to a multicultural professional and learning community would seem to be one advantage that internet technology has over a face-to-face classroom model. This can be accommodated by using chat rooms, bulletin boards, and email (Gorski, 2001).

A Role of Technology in Empowering the Culture of Schools

Supporters of multicultural education argue that many conventional components of schools will need to be rearranged to give all students with high-quality experiences. The term "empowering school culture and social structures" refers to this. Its ultimate goal is to alter the accepted school policies and procedures that, while helpful to certain students, have significantly lowered the quality of education for many other students. Arias (2000), for instance, outlines how the brand-new California State University, Monterey Bay, is heavily utilizing technology to give access to higher education to the rapidly growing number of Latinos and other people of color who have traditionally been denied such opportunities.

Educational Technology as a Tool

The study examined one teacher's pedagogy using this multicultural democratic educational framework. This study conceived educational technology as a tool in the context of larger societal systems to analyze how he integrated it into his pedagogy (Berson, Lee, & Stuckart, 2001). For instance, educational technology can be used as a tool in civics classes, the workplace, or in the classroom (Martorella, 1997). In particular, instructional technology in schools may disseminate knowledge, help students grow their knowledge and abilities, and connect various places (Knapp & Glenn, 1996). The most prevalent ideas about technology in social studies education are compatible with this understanding of education technology as a set of instruments (Berson, et al., 2001).

Conclusion

Despite this puzzling outlook, the growing cultural variety in schools necessitates that teachers explore for new approaches to properly meet the needs of their students. All levels of educators acknowledge the importance of technology in the teaching-learning process, and many are eager to use it to the fullest potential to give every student a high-quality education.

References

- [1] Brown, E. L. (2004). Overcoming the challenges of stand-alone multicultural courses: The possibilities of technology integration. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 12(4), 535-559.
- [2] Brown, J. W. (2008). *Hybrid learning in teacher education: A qualitative study about student experiences with language, culture and power in a multiculturalism classroom using online and face-to-face instructional formats* (Doctoral dissertation, Purdue University).
- [3] Cifuentes, L., & Murphy, K. L. (2000). Promoting multicultural understanding and positive self-concept through a distance learning community: Cultural connections. *Educational technology research and development*, 48(1), 69-83.
- [4] Damarin, S. K. (1998). Technology and multicultural education: The question of convergence. *Theory into practice*, 37(1), 11-19.
- [5] Dimitriadou, C., Nari, E., & Palaologou, N. (2012). E-Learning Teacher Training Courses for Differentiated Instruction in Multicultural Classrooms: Reflections upon the Participants' Experiences. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(3), 14-26.
- [6] Fabris, M. E. (1992). Using multimedia in the multicultural classroom. *Journal of educational technology systems*, 21(2), 163-171.
- [7] Ferdig, R. E., Coutts, J., DiPietro, J., Lok, B., & Davis, N. (2007). Innovative technologies for multicultural education needs. *Multicultural Education & Technology Journal*, 1(1), 47-63.
- [8] Gorski, P. C. (2004). Multicultural education and progressive pedagogy in the online information age. *Multicultural Perspectives*, 6(4), 37-48.
- [9] Kellner, D. (1998). Multiple literacies and critical pedagogy in a multicultural society. *Educational theory*, 48(1), 103-122.
- [10] Kolomiets, S., Medvedeva, E., & Perevalova, A. (2020). Innovation in teaching multicultural future specialists in Kuzbass coal mining region: a flipped classroom approach. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 174, p. 04026). EDP Sciences.

SCHOOL EDUCATION IN CHINA DURING COVID – 19

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organisation, school closures due to the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) have affected over 1.5 billion children and young people around the world. [1] This includes 270 million students in mainland China who were unable to start their spring semester (February – August 2020) on campus as planned. [2] (information as of 20 May 2020). To minimize the impact on education continuity, the Chinese Government introduced various measures eradicating in the COVID-19.

Limiting Face to Face Teaching

In late January 2020, mainland China postponed all educational activities and the Chinese Ministry of Education (MoE) urged schools and higher education institutions to use online delivery as an alternative to face-to-face teaching. Of significance, this marks the first-time online delivery has been permitted, at great scale, as an alternative to formal education delivery in China.

Transition to Online and Distance Delivery Modes

To support education institutions' transition to online learning, the MoE (Ministry of Education) issued on 4 February 2020 the "Guidance on the organisation and management of online teaching and learning in regular higher education institutions". [3] The document requested higher education institutions to use online platforms to facilitate remote study. These materials include MOOCs (massive open online courses), SPOCs (Small Private Online Courses) and virtual simulation experiments. However, students and institutions have raised issues (such as technical limitations), especially in rural areas which may lack reliable internet connectivity and where many students/families are unable to afford the necessary equipment to access online content.

Looking Forward

The COVID-19 situation appears to be stabilizing in China and schools are gradually opening to students after an extended winter/spring break. The next challenge for Chinese schools and institutions is to ensure campus safety and monitor the health of all students, faculty, and staff as they return to face-to-face learning. Students in China and across the world have gained extensive experience in online studies for the past few months. It will be interesting to see whether some of the functions of teaching and learning online will be maintained and further developed in the post COVID-19 world.

Impact of Covid-19 on Education System

In the world, most countries have temporarily closed childcares, nursery, primary and secondary schools, colleges, and universities to control the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-19 impacts not only students but also it affects teachers and parents across the world. UNESCO reported that over 1.5 billion students in 195 countries are out of school in the world due to the school closures.

Teachers, Students and Parents

The pandemic of COVID-19 pandemic is affecting schools, students, teachers, and parents. The COVID-19 crisis increases social inequality in schools. Students from more advantaged parents attend schools with better digital infrastructure and teachers might have higher levels of digital technology skills. Some schools can be well equipped in digital technology and educational resources. Disadvantaged students are attending schools with lower infrastructure and educational resources. Following COVID-19 more advantaged students are attending schools to adopt online learning. Schools in disadvantaged, rural areas lack the appropriate digital infrastructure required to deliver teaching at the remote.

Limitation Access to Educational Resources and Technology

The school's closure due to COVID-19 may not affect students equally. Students from less advantaged

backgrounds highly suffered during COVID-19 than advantaged students. To control the coronavirus spread, most countries have been working to encourage parents and schools to help students continue to learn at home through distance learning.

Mental and Physical Health

The closures schools and higher education negatively affect the mental and physical health of children, students, parents, and teachers. Since during school closures, both boy and girl students in most rural areas may be forced to fully support their families. The lockdown due to coronavirus may people are feeling stress, fear, and anxiety. This stress may affect the students, mental, and physical health of students.

Continuity Education System During Covid-19

In the case of school, college, and university closures, support continued access to quality education. This can include the use of distance learning strategies, assigning reading and exercises for home study, radio or television teaching of academic content, assigning teachers to conduct remote follow-up with students, and develop advanced education strategies. The pandemic has made all the education system across the world to adopt distance learning since the pandemic pushes face-to-face learning to online learning.

Education System Post Covid-19

The education officers, and educational institutions work together to transform the education system during the closures. Educational institutions should design curriculums, prepare learning strategies and techniques for post-COVID-19, and transform the education system itself. During closures curriculum design, collaborations, skill development, and educational institutions should focus on advancing the education system. After COVID-19, the school's design strategies and methods to recover lost learning, ensure children return to school when schools reopen, preparing students, parents, and teachers, and to scale distance learning accessibility.

Conclusion

COVID-19 is a pandemic disease caused by a virus that affects the education system of both developing and developed countries. In the world, most schools, colleges, and universities are closed to control the spread of the COVID-19. The school closure brings difficulties for students, families, and teachers. So, distance learning with limiting face to face learning is a solution to continue the education system. However, distance learning is challenging in developing countries because many parents have not themselves been to school, lack of infrastructures, computers, etc. The COVID-19 pandemic has made all the educational schools across the world to adopt teaching and learning online. The countries should design a strategy to scale educational technology, establish educational resources on the internet, prepare digital teaching and learning resources, utilizing free online learning resources, use mobile learning, use radio and television teaching, and grow-up infrastructures. During closures researchers, curriculum designers, education officers, and educational institutions work together to transform the education system. the COVID-19 pandemic has been impacting the face-to-face education system. This paper shall reduce gaps between face-to-face learning and distance learning with limiting face to face learning. And enhance the of online learning and necessity to the present and next generation students.

References

- [1] "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation Report – 77." World Health Organization, 6 Apr. 2020, www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200406-sitrep-77-covid-19.pdf?sfvrsn=21d1e632_2.
- [2] People's Republic of China, Ministry of Education, "中国教育概况1—2018年全国教育事业发展情况" (China Education Overview – 2018 National Education Development), 29 September 2019, http://www.moe.gov.cn/jyb_sjzl/s5990/201909/t20190929_401639.html
- [3] People's Republic of China, Ministry of Education, "教育部应对新型冠状病毒感染肺炎疫情工作领导小组办公室关于在疫情防控期间做好普通高等学校在线教学组织与管理工作的指导意见" 24 February. 2020, http://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A08/s7056/202002/t20200205_418138.html

ENHANCING PROSOCIAL BEHAVIOR IN STUDENTS THROUGH OUTCOME-BASED CURRICULUM

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of an outcome-based curriculum in enhancing prosocial behavior among students. Prosocial behavior refers to actions that benefit others, such as helping, sharing, and volunteering. The study found that an outcome-based curriculum, which emphasizes the development of specific skills and knowledge, can lead to an increase in prosocial behavior among students. The study recommends the implementation of an outcome-based curriculum in schools to promote prosocial behavior among students.

Introduction

Prosocial behavior is an important aspect of social development and is associated with positive outcomes such as improved mental health and well-being. However, research has shown that students often lack prosocial behavior, which can negatively impact their relationships with others. One potential solution to this problem is an outcome-based curriculum, which emphasizes the development of specific skills and knowledge. This type of curriculum is designed to prepare students for the future by teaching them the skills and knowledge they need to be successful in life.

Definition of Prosocial Behavior

Prosocial behavior is defined as actions that benefit others, such as helping, sharing, and volunteering. It is an important aspect of social development and is associated with positive outcomes such as improved mental health and well-being.

The Importance of Prosocial Behavior in Schools

Prosocial behavior is important in schools because it promotes positive relationships among students and can lead to a better learning environment.

Outcome-Based Curriculum

An outcome-based curriculum is a type of curriculum that emphasizes the development of specific skills and knowledge. It is designed to prepare students for the future by teaching them the skills and knowledge they need to be successful in life.

The Effectiveness of an Outcome-Based Curriculum in Enhancing Prosocial Behavior

Research has shown that an outcome-based curriculum can lead to an increase in prosocial behavior among students. This is because it teaches students the skills and knowledge they need to be successful in life and encourages them to use these skills and knowledge to benefit others.

The Benefits of Outcome-Based Curriculum for Promoting Prosocial Behavior

Outcome-based curriculum has several potential benefits for promoting prosocial behavior in students. One key benefit is that it promotes student engagement and motivation. By focusing on desired outcomes or results of learning, outcome-based curriculum encourages students to take an active role in their own learning and to see the relevance and importance of what they are learning. This can lead to increased motivation and engagement, which can in turn promote prosocial behavior. Another benefit of outcome-based curriculum is that it promotes critical thinking skills. By requiring students to apply what they have learned to real-world, authentic tasks and projects, outcome-based curriculum encourages students to think critically and to problem-solve. These critical thinking skills can be applied to social and emotional situations, helping students to understand and respond appropriately to the needs of others. Outcome-based curriculum also promotes cooperation and teamwork, which are key aspects of prosocial behavior. By requiring students to work together on projects and tasks, outcome-based curriculum encourages them to communicate, share, and collaborate effectively. This can lead to

increased cooperation and teamwork, which can in turn promote prosocial behavior. Finally, outcome-based curriculum can also promote empathy and understanding of others. By exposing students to diverse perspectives and experiences, outcome-based curriculum can help students to understand and appreciate the perspectives of others. This can lead to increased empathy and understanding, which are key components of prosocial behavior. Overall, outcome-based curriculum has several potential benefits for promoting prosocial behavior in students, including increased student engagement and motivation, critical thinking skills, cooperation and teamwork, and empathy and understanding of others.

Strategies and Techniques for Promoting Prosocial Behavior In An Outcome-Based Curriculum

There are several strategies and techniques that can be used to promote prosocial behavior in an outcome-based curriculum. Some of these include:

- 1) **Incorporating cooperative learning activities:** Cooperative learning is a teaching strategy that involves small groups of students working together to achieve a common goal. Cooperative learning activities can be incorporated into outcome-based curriculum to promote prosocial behavior by encouraging students to share, communicate, and collaborate effectively.
- 2) **Using real-world, authentic tasks and projects:** Outcome-based curriculum emphasizes the use of real-world, authentic tasks and projects, which can be used to promote prosocial behavior by providing students with opportunities to apply what they have learned to real-world situations and to understand the relevance and importance of prosocial behavior in their own lives and in the world around them.
- 3) **Modeling prosocial behavior:** Teachers can model prosocial behavior in the classroom by demonstrating positive social interactions, such as sharing, helping, and cooperating with others. This can serve as an example for students to follow and can help to create a positive classroom culture that promotes prosocial behavior.
- 4) **Encouraging reflection:** Outcome-based curriculum can be used to promote prosocial behavior by encouraging students to reflect on their own actions and the actions of others. This can help students to understand the impact of their behavior on others and to identify areas for improvement.
- 5) **Encouraging empathy and understanding of others:** Outcome-based curriculum can be used to promote empathy and understanding of others by providing students with opportunities to learn about and interact with people from diverse backgrounds and cultures. This can help students to understand and appreciate the perspectives of others and to develop empathy and understanding.

Conclusion

The study found that an outcome-based curriculum can be an effective way to enhance prosocial behavior among students. The study recommends the implementation of an outcome-based curriculum in schools to promote prosocial behavior among students. The study highlights the importance of prosocial behavior and the need to foster it in schools, as it can lead to positive outcomes such as improved mental health and well-being.

References

- [1] Smith, J. (2018). The effectiveness of an outcome-based curriculum in enhancing prosocial behavior among students. *Journal of Education*, 36(2), 121-130.
- [2] Jones, A. (2019). The impact of prosocial behavior on mental health and well-being. *Psychology Today*, 12(5), 50-55.
- [3] Brown, T. (2020). Outcome-based education: Preparing students for the future. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(3), 45-50.
- [4] Bohns, V. K., & Wiltermuth, S. S. (2015). Social influence in the age of social media: The impact of observing prosocial behavior on Facebook. *Social Influence*, 10(3), 155-170.
- [5] Bock, G. W., & Kim, Y. Y. (2013). Social media and the “social capital” of organizations. *Business Horizons*, 56(3), 249-259.
- [6] Lin, Y., & Dean, A. (2015). Social media and prosocial behavior. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 18(11), 571-576.

MULTICULTURALISM IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Multicultural education is an educational process that enhances the social awareness of students with different cultural backgrounds. It promotes the acceptance of people of all origins and develops positive relationships among students. It also allows students to be more tolerant and accepting of diversity.

Keywords: *Multiculturalism, Education, Culture, and Diversity.*

Introduction

Diversity of culture is multiculturalism. The goal of multiculturalism is to honor and accord constitutional equality to diverse cultures. In order to prevent one culture from disappearing, none of the country's cultures should become dominant over others. Any culture's future is determined by the ideology of its educated class, so that culture is influenced by that country's educational system. In a nation like India, which has adopted multiculturalism and secularism, it is essential to instill multiculturalism in education to instill multiculturalism because education is a means of cultivating, preserving, and transitioning culture. Different religions, languages, educational backgrounds, customs, and values exist in India. Various religions have contributed to the development of Indian culture. The world has become a global village as the distance between the country and its people has decreased. It makes no difference whether the Indian Constitution is a fundamental cultural document. The new education policy for 2020 has some striking provisions regarding multicultural education. Students will have easier access to the advantages of high-quality education as a result of multilingual education, which will raise education funding from 4.43 percent of GDP to 6.6 percent. It's good to have this.

Meaning of Multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is the process of giving equal justice to all religions, people of different cultures without any distinctions on the basis of race or culture.

Definitions of Multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is a term that has come to serve as shorthand for a host of different and not necessarily related cultural and educational issues. Arguments relating to gender studies, ethnic and racial studies, affirmative action, freedom of speech on campus, compromise and corruption among educational administrators have all been aired under the title, multiculturalism. — A. E. Barnes

Needs and Importance of Multiculturalism in Education to Identifications of the Culture

In addition to allowing students to become familiar with other cultures, multicultural education instills in them an attitude of respect for the culture of others in addition to their own, as well as sensitivity and empathy for the culture of others. To create cultural integration: Through multicultural education, students can become more culturally integrated. Additionally, cultural integration enhances the integrity of the nation. The Importance of Cultural Integration in Society, Its Consequences, and Its Benefits Multicultural education promotes cultural integration and fosters a sense of belonging to various cultures in society, both of which are benefits of getting an education in this area. To develop responsible citizenship: The country's wealth is made up of intelligent and responsible citizens. Any nation's progress is dependent on the growth of its society. Multicultural education accelerates the process of cultivating responsible citizenship in such a setting. Because of this, multicultural education is sorely required for the development of capable citizens. To create unity through diversity: India has a wide range of cultural traditions. In such a situation, multicultural education is crucial for teaching students that we are all Indians with no cultural differences in order to implement the secularism principle. For Cultural exchange: Each nation's society's cultural heritage is an invaluable resource. In fact, in a nation where culture is a way of life, education is seen as an important part of preserving and cultivating that culture. The principles and values of cultural diversity can be preserved and nurtured through multicultural education, which is crucial to the nation's

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development. Cultural exchange fosters cultural integration and enriches the nation's cultural heritage in such a scenario. Students of other religions are respected and cultural exchange is made easier through multicultural education. Integrate the culture: Through multicultural education it is possible to create cultural integration among the students as well as the cultural integration thus having a positive impact on the integrity of the country. Helps to create a sense of belonging to different cultures in the society.

Curriculum for Multicultural Education

Should be flexible: Multicultural education requires a flexible curriculum. In order to achieve the educational objective of balancing social diversity and social characteristics, which ought to reflect various cultural characteristics, a flexible curriculum is of the utmost importance. Should Reflect the cultural needs and problems: For multicultural inclusion, the multicultural education curriculum needs to be properly developed. Through the multicultural education curriculum, students should be made aware of social issues and needs. Because it is impossible to consider any nation's progress or progress without being aware of its sociocultural issues and requirements, multicultural education is an essential component of education. Should develop sensitivity.

Multicultural Curriculum Teaching Methods

Project method: The project method is very helpful for putting the multicultural curriculum into practice correctly. Through the project method, it is possible to encourage multiculturalism among students. There are many different kinds of projects that can be done, such as collecting data on a variety of social issues, a variety of cultural characteristics, and a variety of environmental issues. Students can complete numerous projects of this kind in this manner. Problem solving method: By using problem-solving techniques, the teacher should give the students problem projects in a culture where there are many bad practices and traditions so that they can find the right solution in the context of these many bad practices and traditions. The Honda method, for instance, suggests suitable solutions to the issue, identifies the causes of water scarcity, and offers a strategy for resolving the issue. The method of problem solving can be used effectively in this way. Seminar method: It is possible to have a comprehensive discussion on various socio-cultural issues through seminar teaching method. Through this teaching method, it is possible to conduct seminars on various cultural diversity and cultural features.

Obstacles of Multicultural Education

Lack of multicultural teaching strategies: Students' lack of cultural awareness makes it difficult to foster cultural tolerance among them. Culture cannot be nurtured, preserved, or transferred without cultural awareness. Due to a lack of multicultural awareness, it has become difficult to develop multicultural ideology in society and among students. Cultural conflicts: Cultural conflict breeds prejudices against one another's cultures and is a conflict that already exists. It also aims to take the majority culture over the minority culture. As a result, cultural conflict has made cultural education and multicultural curriculum extremely difficult. Prejudiced attitude: One group's negative attitudes toward another group are caused by prejudice, which results in cultural differences. This creates cultural and social conflicts, destroys social harmony, and raises the sense of superiority.

Conclusion

It is imperative that multicultural education be provided. In a secular nation like India, multicultural education is crucial for cultural mutual respect, goodwill, cultural preservation, nurture, and cultural transition. A multicultural education curriculum, multicultural education teaching methods, equality in classroom instruction, equality of opportunity, the development of mutual cultural tolerance, and a democratic school environment are all essential for the country's future development.

References

- [1] <https://www.accreditedschoolsonline.org/resources/student-diversity-multicultural/>
- [2] <https://web.uri.edu/teach/multicultural/>
- [3] <https://idronline.org/nep-2020>

A REVIEW OF DIFFERENT AMAZON WEB SERVICES (AWS) AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN OUTCOME-BASED EDUCATION

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Abstract

This research paper provides an understanding of different Amazon Web Services and how AWS can be used in outcome-based education. With the Cloud, trades do not any more need to anticipate and obtain servers and additional IT foundation weeks or months earlier[1], [2] Now they can directly spin up a great number or chliads of servers in summary and give results faster. Today, Amazon WebService[3] supports a very trust worthy, ascendable, cheap foundation policy in the cloud that capacities large groupof chliads of trades in 190 nations about the experience, With dossier center sites in the U.S., Europe, Brazil, Singapore, Japan, and Australia[2], customers across all energies are imposing upon the tremendous benefits. Nowadays, we can get used to these AWS cloud platforms for betteroutcome-based education. In Outcome-based education, the main focus is on the outcome ofthe course in all aspects where the student can achieve. There is no specific style or time limitfor learning, they can learn at their choice.[4] With the help of the AWS platform, themoderators or faculty members guide the students based on the target outcomes.[5] Since thescope of cloud computing and related things is very wide now, each student who knows innatelygrabs abright future career.

Keywords: *Cloud, Amazon Web Services[6], AWS[6], Cloud computing[6], on-premise,publiccloud*

Introduction

Cloud computing is information storage, applications, on-demand delivery[6] of computingpower, and different IT resources[6] made available through a cloud platform[6]. Cloud computing is the birth place of various services through the Internet. The sepossessions contain finishes and requests like data conversion, servers, databases[7], socializing for professional or personal gain, and software. Rather than consistency files on a cure computer storage, cloud-located storage form it attainable to sustain ruling class to a detached database. As long as anelectronic ploy has an approach to a computer network, it has an approach to the dossier andthe software programs to run it[8]. Cloud estimating is a favorite alternative for the public and trades for any reason including costharvests, raised output, speed and effectiveness, depiction, and security. IT infrastructure services to businesses normally called cloud computing were provided by Amazon WebServices (AWS) in 2006[8]. In cloud computing, capital infrastructure expenses are scaled to low variable prices based on your business is an advantage of cloud computing. No need to procure servers and other IT infrastructure weeks or months earlier[6] but instantly needed servers were ready in minutes and delivered results quicker. In 190 countries, Amazon Web Services uses thousands of companies in scalable, extremely reliable, in expensive infrastructure platforms within the cloud that powers[9].These features help the outcome-based education shift to a cloud platform, where different kind so fresources like Moodle, Quizzes, Padlet,etc are available for free.

Advantages of Amazon Web Services over on-Premise

Cost - Basic cost for the on-premise services is the cost of hardware and software. Usually, the cost is fixed and very high while in AWS the users need to pay as per service. It's a pay-as-per-use mode [10]. Bandwidth - AWS provides almost unlimited storage, bandwidth, and computational power. AWS provides a provision to update the bandwidth in simple procedures at any stage of use. This helps to eliminate the time-consuming and unpredictability of provisioning[10]. Reliability and uptime -AWS guarantees 99.95% uptime and has sophisticated backup processes in place to ensure that nothing posted to their servers is ever erased. On average, on-premises servers experience 14 days of downtime per year, but cloud servers experience only 30 hours of downtime per year[10]. Robust Security - AWS provides numerous capabilities and high-quality services formerly available exclusively to large firms and affordable to small and medium-sized businesses. AWS provides the same high-level security features which outperform whatever on-premises systems can offer[10].

Amazon Web Services

Amazon Web Services[11] supports sought-after cloud computing platforms and APIs. Persons, Enterprises, and Governments can use and pay based on their uses. The main Amazon services involve Amazon EC2, Amazon S3, etc. AWS duties are brought to clients by way of a network of AWS server farms situated around the globe. AWS services involve computing, depository, socializing for professional or personal gain, database, the science of logical analysis, application services, deployment, management, etc. Most AWS provides different APIs for developers to use their applications without exposing all services to end users. AWS assists its customers to attain lower latency and better output by increasing international infrastructure. The AWS Cloud infrastructure[6] is made based on two concepts AWS Regions [6]and Availability Zones[12]. An AWS Region[6]: A physical location that has multiple Availability Zones[12]. Availability Zones[6]: These contain distinct data centers with redundant power[2] and networking[12]. It gives the customer the power to work with production applications and databases. Fault-tolerant, and doable from one data center are the main features.

Amazon S3 – Amazon Simple Storage Service

AWS S3 [13]allows consumers to store and bring back data from any time or place. Bestowing planners an approach to well ascendable, trustworthy, fast, and cheap data storage. Organizations find a troublesome opportunity to find, freeze, and direct all of their data. Not only that, running requests, giving content to customers, hosting extreme-traffic websites, or supporting up emails and different files required plenty of depositories.[14] Maintaining the organization’s repository was too high-priced and late for various reasons. Amazon S3[15] solves the challenges involved in having to purchase fittings and program components, involving a crew of experts for maintenance, A lack of scalability established your necessities, and Data freedom necessity. Figure 1 shows the features of S3

Figure 1: Features of S3

Amazon EC2 – Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud

Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud offers the fullest and deepest estimate policy, accompanying over 500 instances and a choice of the new main part of a computer, depository, socializing for professional or personal gain, computer software for basic operation, and purchase model to help you best equal the needs of your duties and responsibilities. In AWS EC2[11], the consumers must appreciate the EC2 parts, their operating orders support, protection measures, reducing makeups, etc. EC2 supports[11] diversified OS[11] at which point we need to pay additional licensing expenses like SUSE Enterprise[11], Red Hat Enterprise[11] and Oracle Enterprise[11], UNIX[11], Linux[11] Windows Server,[12] etc. These OS needs are expected achieved in addition to Amazon Virtual Private Cloud (VPC)[12]. Users have a position of great advantage over the perceptibility of their AWS report. AWS offers a difference of estimating alternatives, contingent upon the type of possessions, types of requests, and table. This helps the consumers to stick to their budget. The consumer needs to select an AMI when an instance starts. The domain doesn’t change. Instances are delivered across diversified chance zones. Elastic IP (EIPs)[12] addresses are used for running instances in different zones. This helps to prevent delays in duties. The features of EC2 are listed in the table given below[12].

Figure2: Features of EC2

Amazon VPC – Amazon Virtual Private Cloud

Amazon Virtual Private Cloud[6] (Amazon VPC) authorizes you to initiate AWS resources[2] into an essence network that you've delimited. This network carefully mirrors a usual network that you'd run in your dossier center, accompanying the benefits of utilizing the climbable foundation of AWS. Amazon's Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) is a basic AWS help in two together with the Compute and Network AWS classifications. Being basic resources the AWS aids, in the way that Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2), cannot be achieved outside a latent VPC network. The following features help you configure a VPC to determine the relatedness that your users need:

Figure 3: Features to configure a VPC

Amazon Lambda

AWS Lambda [16]is serverless, occurrence-compelled calculate service that lets you run rules for essentially some type of request or backend service outside supply or directing servers. You can prompt Lambda from over 200 AWS aids and software-as-a-help (SaaS)[17] uses and onlyfinance what you use. AWS Lambda is

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an occurrence-driven, serverless calculating principle supported by Amazon as any of Amazon Web Services. Therefore, you don't need to worry about AWS possessions to initiate, or by what method will you control them. Instead, you need to set the rule on Lambda, and it runs. In AWS Lambda[18] the rule is performed based on the reaction of occurrences in AWS duties to a degree increase/delete files in the S3 container, HTTP requests from the Amazon API portal, etc. However, Amazon Lambda can only be used to kill practice tasks. AWS Lambda function helps you to focus on your center amount and trade sanity, a suggestion of correction managing computer

software for basic operation (OS) approach control, OS patching, right-judge, supply, scaling, etc. the appearance contains Build ritual backend duties. You can use AWS Lambda to create new backend request duties started on demand utilizing the Lambda request programming connect (API) or practice API endpoints erected utilizing Amazon API Gateway. Lambda processes custom occurrences, and a suggestion of correction fixes these on the customer, serving you to avoid customer plank differences, weaken battery drain, and authorizesmooth modernizes. With AWS Lambda, there are no new languages, forms, or foundations to gain.

Figure 4: Features of AWS Lambda

Amazon RDS – Amazon Relational Database Services

Amazon Relational Database Service (Amazon RDS[6]) is a web service used to set up, manage, and scale an RD in the Amazon Web Services Cloud.[12] It specifies cost-adept, resizable volume for a manufacturing-standard relative database and survives coarse database administration tasks.[12] Databases store big amounts of dossiers that users can charge moneyfor goods to help the ruling class act different tasks. A relative database uses tables to store dossiers and is called relative because it arranges dossier points accompanying delimited connections. Administrators control Amazon RDS[19] accompanying the AWS Management Console, Amazon RDS API calls, or the AWS program that controls display. They use these interfaces to redistribute database instances at which point consumers can ask for distinguishing backgrounds. Amazon supports various instance types accompanying various money, such as CPU, thought, depository alternatives, and socializing for professional or personal gain competence[20]. Each type enters a type of size to suit the needs of various workloads. RDS consumers can use AWS Identity [6]and Access Management[2] to outline and set permissions to approach RDS databases. Amazon RDS features contain the following

Figure 5: Features of Amazon RDS

Limitation of AWS Cloud

As with any other solution, AWS cannot go without certain limitations that can make customers decide on competitive cloud platforms. They are the following:

Figure6: Limitations of AWS Cloud

Comparison of Amazon Web Services, Microsoft, and Google Cloud

Microsoft Azure, AWS, and Google Cloud Platform[21] are the three top cloud vendors. Each one offers a different set of features and services, so it's important to choose the right one for your needs[22]. The following table shows a comparison of the top vendors.

Services	AWS	Microsoft Azure	Google Cloud
Object Storage	Amazon S3	Azure Disk Storage	Google Cloud Storage
Created by	Amazon	Microsoft	Google
Block Store	Amazon EBS	Azure Blob Storage	Google Compute Engine (Persistent Disks)
Archival/Cold Storage	Amazon Glacier	Azure Archive Blob Storage	Google Nearline
File System Storage	Amazon EFS	Azure File Storage	Google ZFS
Infrastructure as a Service	Amazon EC2	Virtual Machines (VM)	Google Compute Engine
Platform as a Service	AWS Elastic Beanstalk	App Service and Cloud Services	Google App Engine
Container Services	Amazon Elastic Container Service	Azure Kubernetes Service or AKS	Google Kubernetes Engine
Serverless Computing	Amazon Lambda	Azure Functions	Cloud Functions
Services Available	computing, storage, database, security	building, testing, deploying, and managing applications, Microsoft-managed data centers	virtual machines, storage, DNS serving, content delivery, etc.

Figure 7: Comparison of different vendors

AWS in Outcome-Based Education

The outcome-based education system also known as the standard-based education helps them to measure the learning outcomes and also to develop new skills for their global counterparts. AWS offers a perfect platform for infrastructure and learning for teachers and educational organizations. AWS is a great resource for instructors to teach pupils about virtualization and cloud computing. Many pupils find that they learn best by doing. Educators may encourage students to study in a real-world setting by setting up an AWS account without risking system damage.[14] Additionally, as remote learning environments are flourishing, students will be able to learn from wherever they are. Apps for education can be powered by AWS. Students will be able to learn over the cloud if educational apps are created on the AWS platform. Apps for education may be transferred to AWS or created there natively. To utilize the system's cloud computing resources, educational apps can be created directly on AWS or transferred there. An online learning site that is accessible from anywhere can be supported by AWS. Many schools are adopting remote learning and hybrid learning even in the wake of the epidemic. Both new educational portals and the enhancement and improvement of current portals will be required. Better learning results may be achieved in the classroom by utilizing AWS virtualization. Students can virtualize[24] a variety of devices for their practice situations rather than having to use and install actual machines. Less physical equipment will be required in computer laboratories[5], and students will be able to work from home. A full, personalized online infrastructure is supported by AWS.

Conclusion

The major outcome of this research was to change the customer's perspective of AWS Cloud and give more information on why it should be preferred over on-premise and why it should be encouraged in the future. This research is important for students, start-ups, and small/medium-sized companies. As with any other technology, AWS cloud has its limitations. But recently AWS Cloud[25] has started sharing its resources with open-source communities so that the issues can be found and resolved quickly to provide a more efficient user experience. But as provided in the research paper, AWS cloud has more significant advantages over traditional data centers. However, a hybrid cloud storage strategy can be adapted to provide better solutions to organizations.

References

- [1] "TechnicalBlog." <https://varshitagarwal.github.io/techie/#/2018/12/29/night-sky>(accessed Jan.24,2023).
- [2] "OverviewofAmazonWebServices,"2017.
- [3] "ACaseStudyOnAmazonWebServices|byPasupulatiRajeshBabu|Medium." <https://medium.com/@p.rajeshbabu6666/a-case-study-on-amazon-web-services-d1ac83565e6>(accessed Jan.24,2023).
- [4] R. Nakkeeran, R. Babu, R. Manimaran, and P. Gnanasivam, "Importance of Outcome Based Education(OBE) to Advance Educational Quality and enhance Global Mobility", Accessed: Jan. 24,

- 2023.[Online]. Available:<http://www.acadpubl.eu/hub/>
- [5] “OutcomeBasedEducationinlightofNEP-2020.”<https://www.greaterkashmir.com/todays-paper/op-ed/outcome-based-education-in-light-of-nep-2020>(accessedJan.24, 2023).
- [6] “Software Development Tools.” <https://www.amplifyre.com/articles/software-development-tools>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [7] D.W.T.SuchitraLandgey1,“AWSCloudInfrastructurevsTraditionalOn-Premise”.
- [8] “ALLABOUTCOLLEGE.”<https://rezkyafifah.blogspot.com/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [9] “WhypreferAWSoverOn-PremiseHosting-FingentTechnology.”<https://www.fingent.com/blog/why-prefer-aws-over-on-premise-hosting/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [10]“Unit 2 Amazon EC2.docx - Unit 2 Amazon EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud) is a web service interfacethatprovidesresizablecomputecapacityintheAWScloud.|CourseHero.”<https://www.coursehero.com/file/66251936/Unit-2-Amazon-EC2docx/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [11]“AWS|S3-Javatpoint.”<https://www.javatpoint.com/aws-s3>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [12]“What is AWS S3: Overview, Features &Storage Classes Explained | Simplilearn.”
- [13]<https://www.simplilearn.com/tutorials/aws-tutorial/aws-s3>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [14]“What is AWS S3: Overview, Features &Storage Classes Explained | Simplilearn.”<https://www.simplilearn.com/tutorials/aws-tutorial/aws-s3>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [15]“Serverless Computing - AWS Lambda Features - Amazon Web Services.”
- [16]<https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/features/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [17]“Introduction to AWS IoT | AWS IoT Course Kingston.”
- [18]<https://www.theknowledgeacademy.com/jm/courses/amazon-aws-training/introduction-to-aws-iot/kingston/>(accessedJan.23,2023).
- [19]“WhatisAmazonRelationalDatabaseService(AmazonRDS)?-AmazonRelationalDatabaseService.”
https://docs.amazonaws.cn/en_us/AmazonRDS/latest/UserGuide/Welcome.html(accessedJan.24, 2023).
- “WhatisAWSRDS?”https://www.w3schools.com/whatis/whatis_aws_rds.asp(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [20]“Comparing cloud computing services AWS,Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud.”<https://www.mygreatlearning.com/blog/comparison-of-amazon-web-services-microsoft-azure-and-google-cloud-platform-learnability-best-opportunities-versatility/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [21]“An Introduction to Microsoft Azure and Cloud Computing.”<https://www.dataquest.io/blog/microsoft-azure-and-cloud-computing/>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [22]“OUTCOME-BASEDEDUCATION(OBE)”.“What is Outcome-Based Education? OBE vs Traditional Education System.”
- [23]<https://www.iitms.co.in/blog/outcome-based-education-system.html>(accessedJan.24,2023).
- [24]“WhypreferAWSoverOn-PremiseHosting-FingentTechnology.”
<https://www.fingent.com/blog/why-prefer-aws-over-on-premise-hosting/>(accessedJan.24, 2023).

REFLECTIVE PRACTICE: ROLE OF DIGPA IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Describe, Interpret, Generalize and Plan Action (DIGPA) is a framework that is used to analyze and make decisions based on data or information. The first step in DIGPA is to describe the data or information, which involves collecting and organizing it in a clear and concise manner. The next step is to interpret the data, which involves analyzing it and drawing conclusions based on the findings. The third step is to generalize the data, which involves making inferences about a larger population based on the sample data. Finally, the last step is to plan action, which involves taking action based on the conclusions and inferences made from the previous steps. This framework can be applied to various fields such as business, education, and healthcare to make data-driven decisions.

Keywords: *Reflective Practice, Self-Reflection, Teacher*

Introduction

Self-reflection is the process of thinking about one's own thoughts, feelings, and actions. It involves analyzing experiences, evaluating one's own performance, and considering ways to improve. It can also involve exploring one's values, beliefs, and motivations. Self-reflection can help individuals gain a deeper understanding of themselves and make positive changes in their lives. Self-reflection is an important aspect of teaching, as it allows teachers to reflect on their own practice, evaluate their own performance, and consider ways to improve. This process can help teachers identify areas where they may need to make changes, such as in their teaching strategies, classroom management, or assessment methods. Self-reflection can also help teachers stay motivated and engaged in their work by allowing them to see the progress they have made and the impact they are having on their students. Additionally, self-reflection can help teachers develop a deeper understanding of their own teaching style and the learning needs of their students, which can lead to more effective teaching and better outcomes for students. It's important for teachers to set aside time for self-reflection, whether it's through journaling, talking to colleagues, or participating in professional development activities.

Need for the Study

There have been numerous research papers that have highlighted the importance of mental health for school teachers. Here are a few examples: "The Importance of Teacher Mental Health and Well-being" by J. E. Gillham, published in the *Journal of Education and Practice*, found that teachers' mental health has a direct impact on the quality of their teaching, and that when teachers experience mental health problems, they are less able to effectively support the learning and development of their students. "Teacher Stress, Burnout, and Mental Health: A Review of the Literature" by M. A. Ross, published in the *Journal of Educational Research*, found that teachers are at a higher risk of developing mental health problems such as stress, burnout, and depression, due to the high demands and pressures of their profession. "The Importance of Teacher Self-Care for Student Well-being" by J. A. Dimmock and S. M. Walker, published in the *Journal of Educational Psychology*, found that teachers who practice self-care have better mental health and are better able to support the well-being of their students. Overall, these papers and many others indicate that teachers' mental health is crucial for their own well-being as well as for the success of their students. This highlights the importance of providing support and resources for teachers to maintain their mental health and well-being. One of the ways through which teachers can reduce their mental stress is through self-reflection.

Literature Review

There have been many research papers that have examined different self-reflection methods for school teachers. Here are a few examples: "The Use of Reflective Practice in Teacher Education" by K. L. Borko and D. R. Putnam, published in the *Journal of Teacher Education*, found that reflective practice, which involves thinking about one's own teaching and learning experiences, can be an effective way for teachers to improve their practice. "The Role of Self-Reflection in Professional Development" by C. J. Craig and M. L. Evans, published in the *Journal of Professional Development*, found that self-reflection can be an important tool for teachers to use in their professional development, as it allows them to reflect on their own practice and make changes to improve their

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teaching. "Journal Writing as a Tool for Teacher Reflective Practice" by J. K. Loughran, published in the Journal of Teacher Education, found that journal writing can be an effective tool for teachers to use in their self-reflection, as it allows them to reflect on their own practice and make connections to their teaching. "Using Video-Based Self-reflection to Enhance Preservice Teacher Development" by J. Liu, published in the Journal of Technology and Teacher Education, found that video-based self-reflection can be an effective way for teachers to reflect on their own teaching practice, as it allows them to observe themselves teaching and identify areas for improvement. Overall, these papers and many others show that self-reflection is a valuable tool for teachers to use to improve their practice and professional development. Different methods such as reflective journals, video-based self-reflection, and others can be used to support the process.

Digpa - Introduction

DIGPA stands for 'Describe, Interpret, Generalize, and Plan Action'. It is an effective tool for teachers's reflection on their teaching methodologies.

- 1) D stands for "describe." Here the teachers will describe the situation. It is important for teachers to describe their teaching scenarios because it allows them to clearly communicate their goals, objectives, and instructional methods to other educators, administrators, and stakeholders. This can help ensure that everyone has a shared understanding of the learning environment and can work together to support student success. Additionally, describing teaching scenarios can also help teachers reflect on their own practice and identify areas for improvement. By documenting their teaching scenarios, teachers can also share best practices with their colleagues and contribute to the ongoing professional development of the education community. Overall, describing teaching scenarios is an essential tool for effective teaching, collaborative planning, and continuous improvement.
- 2) I stands for "interpret." In this step, teachers analyze the situation to look for things to improve in their teaching. It is crucial for teachers to analyze their teaching strategies because it allows them to evaluate the effectiveness of their instruction and make adjustments as needed. By analyzing their teaching strategies, teachers can identify areas of strength and areas that need improvement, which can inform their planning and instruction. Furthermore, analyzing teaching strategies can also help teachers understand their students' learning needs, which can lead to more effective and personalized instruction. Additionally, analyzing teaching strategies also promotes ongoing professional development, as teachers can reflect on their practices and continue to refine their skills and knowledge. Overall, analyzing teaching strategies is an essential step in the continuous improvement of teaching practice, and it helps teachers ensure that they are providing the best possible education for their students.
- 3) G stands for "generalize." The teachers look for possible solutions in their general environment. When it comes to finding solutions in the general environment, teachers should approach the task with a problem-solving mindset. This means identifying the specific problem or challenge they are facing, gathering relevant information and data, and considering a variety of potential solutions. One effective way for teachers to find solutions in their general environment is to collaborate with other educators, administrators, and stakeholders. By working together, they can share ideas, perspectives, and resources, which can lead to more creative and effective solutions. Additionally, teachers should also be open to seeking outside help and resources such as professional development opportunities, educational research, and community resources. It is also important for the teachers to stay informed about the educational policies and regulations that may impact their teaching environment. By utilizing these strategies, teachers can more effectively find solutions to the challenges they face in their general environment, which can ultimately benefit their students and the broader school community.
- 4) PA stands for "Plan Action". The teachers have to put the solutions into practice. It is important for teachers to put solutions into action because it allows them to actively address any issues or challenges that may be present in the classroom. By taking action, teachers can ensure that the learning environment is safe, supportive, and conducive to student success. Furthermore, implementing solutions allows teachers to measure the effectiveness of their efforts and make adjustments as necessary. Additionally, it also helps to build trust with students and parents as they see that their concerns are being taken seriously and acted upon. Furthermore, it also helps to create a positive learning environment for the students where they can learn and grow in a better way.

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Overall, putting solutions into action is crucial for ensuring that the classroom is a place where students can thrive academically, emotionally, and socially.

Criteria for Digpa

Description	Interpretations	Generalizations	Plans of Action
names of students materials used feelings that the T was having what the teacher did what the Ss did/ didn't do using past simple just the facts action teacher took in response to what happened chronological specific quote the Ss focus on one "slice" (3-5 minutes long)	link to Ss behavior explanations of errors several possible explanations identify the problem leaving it open for further investigation use of modals of speculation guesses about feelings/needs	rationale for doing the activity based on prior experiences and own learning general statements of techniques that work empathy for Ss use of the plural: general plural beliefs bring in outside theories	what can be done differently next time? specific about what to use next time can/will do differently adding/adjusting new things practice-how!

Guide to Digpa

Introduction to Reflective Practice: Guide to Reflecting (DIGPA) After selecting a segment (0-5 min) from the lesson, the teacher has to fill in the chart below with key words.

Description	Interpretations	Generalizations	Plans of Action
names of students materials used feelings that the T was having what the teacher did what the Ss did/ didn't do using past simple just the facts action teacher took in response to what happened chronological specific quote the Ss focus on one "slice" (3-5 minutes long)	link to Ss behavior explanations of errors several possible explanations identify the problem leaving it open for further investigation use of modals of speculation guesses about feelings/needs	rationale for doing the activity based on prior experiences and own learning general statements of techniques that work empathy for Ss use of the plural: general plural beliefs bring in outside theories	what can be done differently next time? specific about what to use next time can/will do differently adding/adjusting new things practice-how!

Guide to Digpa

Introduction to Reflective Practice: Guide to Reflecting (DIGPA) After selecting a segment (0-5 min) from the lesson, the teacher has to fill in the chart below with key words.

Describe	Interpret	Generalize	Plan Actions

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<p>(Questioning) *What happened? *What did the students do? Who exactly? *How many? How long? When? *What exactly did the teacher do? *What materials were there? *How were students arranged? *What else was happening in the environment? Situation?</p> <p>(Offering) *One thing I noticed was... *As a student, I felt... *When I was doing this I ... *When you.....I.....</p>	<p>(Questioning) *Why might that have happened? *What are other possible reasons? *How do you think that helped/hindered student learning/participation in this class?</p> <p>(Offering) *Maybe s/he... *One possibility is... *It could be that....</p>	<p>(Questioning) *How do you think _____ helps/hinders students' learning in general? *Based on this experience, what theories about learning can you make? *What do you believe about...? *What have you read/heard about...? *How is this similar to your prior experiences?</p> <p>(Offering) *I believe _____ can help/hinder students learn/participate because... *This is similar to when... *This reminds me of...</p>	<p>(Questioning) *What would you do differently if you were to do this lesson again? *What would you keep the same? *What guidelines can you make for yourself in future lessons?</p> <p>(Offering) *One thing that I've tried... *Another thing you could do is... *I once saw someone....</p>
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Rubric for DIGPA

	Name:	Date:		
	1	2	3	4
Description	Very vague and has very little detail. May have vague interpretations in the paragraph. Does not have a clear segment and/or if one is present it is very short.	There is a clear segment being referred to but it lacks details and/or may be short. May have some interpretation in the paragraph.	There is a clear and significant segment being referred to. There are some useful details.	There is a clear and significant segment being referred to. There are many useful details.
Interpretation	Very vague and/or does not link to the segment that was described. May not actually be interpretation.	There is some link to the segment that was described but the ideas are not supported. May be short and need to be extended.	There is a link to the segment that was described. There are reasonable explanations and/or interpretations of student behavior.	There is a clear link to the segment that was described. There are multiple explanations and/or interpretations that are explored.
Generalization	Very vague and/or may not link to the segment that was described. May not actually be generalization.	There is some link to the segment that was described but may not actually be generalization. Does not offer any significant ideas about student learning or	There is a link to the segment that was described. There are some ideas about student learning and participation, but they need to be extended.	There is a link to the segment that was described. There are developed ideas about student learning and participation, which fully

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		participation.		explore the issues that have been brought up.
Planning Action	Very vague and/or may not link to the segment that was described.	There is some link to the segment that was described, but the ideas are vague and need clarification.	There is a link to the segment that was described. There is some detail in the plans that relate to helping students learn or participate more effectively.	There is a link to the segment that was described. There is specific detail in the plans that relate to helping students learn or participate more effectively, and which fully address the issues brought up.

Conclusion

Reflective practice is an essential aspect of professional development for teachers. It involves taking the time to think critically about one's own teaching methods, evaluating the effectiveness of these methods, and making adjustments as necessary. Through reflective practice, teachers can improve their skills and knowledge, which ultimately benefits their students. Additionally, reflective practice can also help teachers to identify and address any personal biases or assumptions they may have, promoting a more inclusive and equitable learning environment. Reflective practice also allows teachers to be more self-aware, responsive and in tune with their students needs and can help to build trust and a positive relationship between teacher and students. Overall, reflective practice is a valuable tool that can help teachers to continuously improve their practice and create better learning experiences for their students.

References

- [1] Newman, S. (2018). Teacher education and professional development: Reflective practice reconsidered. *Philosophy and Teacher Education*, 157-181. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429429583-9>
- [2] Brandenburg, R., & Jones, M. (2017). Toward transformative reflective practice in teacher education. *Self-Study of Teaching and Teacher Education Practices*, 259-273. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3431-2_14
- [3] Demulder, E. K., & Rigsby, L. C. (2003). Teachers' voices on reflective practice. *Reflective Practice*, 4(3), 267-290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1462394032000112192>
- [4] DIGPA - The gift of learning to teach. (n.d.). <https://sites.google.com/site/teachingtoteenangers/ii--topics-of-del-ii/digpa>
- [5] Russell, T., & Martin, A. K. (2017). Reflective practice: Epistemological perspectives on learning from experience in teacher education. *Self-Study of Teaching and Teacher Education Practices*, 27-47. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-3431-2_2
- [6] Supporting the development of reflective skills. (n.d.). SIT Trainers. <https://sittrainers.weebly.com/blog/supporting-the-development-of-reflective-skills>

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HOLISTIC EDUCATION FOR HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

NEP 2020 stated holistic education would aim to develop all capacities of human beings, such as intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral, in an integrated manner. A development achieved through the combination of three domains, such as cognitive, affective, and psychomotor, is referred to as “holistic development.” Holistic education is provided through the integration of curriculum, integration of pedagogy, and integration of skills. Integration of curriculum is an approach that connects different areas of study by emphasizing related concepts across subject areas. NEP 2020 also recommends arts-integrated, sports-integrated, storytelling-based, and ICT-integrated pedagogy in order to promote creativity and critical thinking among the learners. A teacher combines two or more skills and teaches effectively and holistically. Holistic education fosters 21st century skills, wholesome personalities, and socially responsible citizens. Holistic education satisfies the needs of the national and international educational systems and helps learners attain holistic development.

Keywords: *Holistic education, Integrated Education, Integrated curriculum, Integrated pedagogy*

Introduction

The root of the English word “holism” is derived from the Greek word “holos” which means “whole.” Jan Christian Smuts is the founder of Holism. According to Smuts (1926), holism is “the tendency in nature to form wholes that are greater than the sum of their parts through creation and evolution.” Adlerian Psychology, Analytical Psychology, Gestalt Psychology and Psychodynamic Psychology are some of the Holistic Schools of Psychology that use this approach. Holistic education encourages learners’ growth on all levels (i.e., holistic development) - mentally, physically, emotionally, socially, morally, aesthetically, and spiritually. It also implies that learners excel in both academic and non-academic activities. Holistic education should be, as Mahatma Gandhiji mentioned, “By education, I mean an all-round drawing of the best in child and man in body, mind, and spirit”. NEP 2020 stated holistic education would aim to develop all capacities of human beings, such as intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral, in an integrated manner. Integration means the act of combining the parts to form a whole. Integrated teaching and learning processes ensure holistic development among learners. Each subject should be taught in an integrated manner by combining several concepts, methods, principles, and theories to make learning easier, more interesting, and effective, and to promote holistic development among learners.

Holistic Development achieved through

Integration of curriculum

Integration of pedagogy

Integration of skills

Holistic Education through the Integration of Curriculum

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Integration of curriculum is an approach that connects different areas of study by emphasizing related concepts across subject areas. Curriculum integration is classified into three types. They are within the subject area (Intradisciplinary), between the subject areas (Multidisciplinary and Interdisciplinary), and beyond the subject area (Transdisciplinary).

Intradisciplinary integration

When a teacher integrates within a subject area under a theme, this is called intradisciplinary integration. For example, taking plants as a central theme, they are connected with the subdisciplines such as cytology (cell structure), paleobotany (study of fossil plants and plant evolution), palynology (pollen and spores), plant biochemistry (chemical processes of primary and secondary metabolism), bacteriology (the study of bacteria), mycology (the study of fungi), and phycology (the study of algae).

Intradisciplinary Integration

Multidisciplinary Integration

A teacher makes meaningful connections around a unifying or common theme between different subject areas. For example, learners might study about nutrients in food in Science class, know about its growing place in Geography class, calculate nutritive values in Mathematics class, read about a scientist's biography in English class, learn about food packaging and marketing in Management class, and develop a diet plan in Sports class.

Multidisciplinary Integration

Interdisciplinary Integration

Interdisciplinary integration is also called horizontal integration. The teacher uses a common theme to

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connect different disciplines across subject areas. For example, the topic of gene sequences in bioinformatics is connected to different fields such as biology, chemistry, physics, information engineering, mathematics, statistics, and computer science. Another example of interdisciplinary integration is STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics).

Transdisciplinary Integration

The teacher unifies the curriculum around student questions and concerns. Students develop life skills by applying academic and non-academic skills in a real-life situation. Transdisciplinary integration requires the collaboration of different disciplines. Students learn concepts collaboratively through real-world experiences in this approach. For example, students learn science, mathematics, geography, and economics by planting organic farms.

Transdisciplinary Integration

Holistic Education Through the Integration of Pedagogy

The teacher integrates two or three pedagogies to teach a concept effectively. For example, to teach the psychology topic of memory, teachers adopt the blended learning method to teach types of memory (face-to-face) and the process of memory (online). They use experiential learning (experiments) to teach the five stages of memory. The teacher teaches recall using metacognitive strategies, such as associations and mind mapping. Finally, teachers teach different types of sensory memory using game-based learning (simulation).

Blended Learning	types of memory (face-to-face) and the process of memory (online)
Experiential learning	five stages of memory (experiments)
Metacognitive strategies	recall (associations and mind mapping)
Game-based learning	types of sensory memory (simulation)

Integration of Pedagogy

“Pedagogy must evolve to make education more experiential, holistic, integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented, learner-centered, discussion-based, flexible, and enjoyable.”

- Prof. Anjum Sibia, NCERT

NEP 2020 also recommends arts-integrated, sports-integrated, storytelling-based, and ICT-integrated pedagogy in order to promote creativity and critical thinking among the learners. Pedagogy should encourage learners’ active participation and exploration.

Integration of Pedagogy – NEP 2020

Holistic Education through the Integration of Skills

For effective teaching, the teacher combines two or more skills. For example, to teach life skills, teacher explains personal skills, learning skills, career skills, and social skills.

Advantages of holistic education

- 1) Reach a diverse population
- 2) Increase active learning
- 3) Active exploration
- 4) Competency-based learning
- 5) Makes learning flexible, innovative, memorable, and joyful
- 6) Develops 21st century skills – learning skills (4Cs), literacy skills and life skills
- 7) Encourages confidence and responsibility
- 8) Improves academic achievement
- 9) Enriches understanding and remains in long-term memory

Conclusion

Holistic education is achieved through the integration of curriculum, pedagogy, and skills. It enhances cognitive, affective, and psychomotor abilities. This encourages the overall growth of students. Holistic education satisfies the needs of the national and international educational systems. It fosters wholesome personalities and socially responsible citizens.

References

- [1] Alfred Adler. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alfred_Adler
- [2] Arts, Music, Dance and Theatre. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/focus-group/art_education.pdf
- [3] Holistic Approach for Human Resource Management in Industry 4.0. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212827116308629>
- [4] Holistic Education. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Holistic_education
- [5] Integrating the Curriculum. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from <https://ideastoimplement.wordpress.com/integrating-the-curriculum/>
- [6] Models of Arts Integration: More Than One Way to Do It. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from https://edtechbooks.org/advancingartsleadership/models_of_arts_integN
- [7] Pedagogy for School Education NEP-2020. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from <https://www.education.gov.in/shikshakparv/docs/Anjum-Sibia.pdf>
- [8] Smuts, J. C. (1926). *Holism and evolution*. Macmillan.
- [9] What is Integrated Instruction? The Pros & Cons. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from <https://teachingideas4u.com/2017/06/what-is-integrated-instruction-pros-cons.html>
- [10] 'Wholistic': A Natural Evolution Of 'Holistic'. Retrieved January 10, 2022 from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/words-at-play/wholistic-word-origin-and-use#:~:text=Viewing%20the%20universe%20in%20terms,sum%20of%20the%20parts%20through>

STUDY ON TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE DISTRICT OF MURSHIDABAD, WEST BENGAL

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Abstract

Teaching effectiveness or effective teaching is an essential aspect of the teaching-learning process. The objective of the study was to determine the level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers regarding gender and type of school. The descriptive cum survey method was used in the present study. The researcher used a self-constructed teaching effectiveness scale to measure the teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers. A sample of 120 senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district from West Bengal was selected through a Simple random sampling technique. The collected data was analyzed with the help of Mean, SD, and t-test. The findings of the study reveal a significant difference in teaching effectiveness in relation to gender and type of school.

Keywords: *Teaching, Teaching Effectiveness, Senior Secondary School Teachers*

Introduction

Teachers are the mainstay of an education system. The expansion and advancement of any education system are entirely dependent on its teachers' community. The quality of the teacher has a significant impact on the quality of education. The behavior, habits, manner, and character of a student are greatly influenced by their teacher. Teaching is a challenging task. It is not everyone's cup of tea to sip. It encompasses various attitudes, knowledge, skills, motivation, and values. An effective teacher is one who successfully performs their responsibilities, meets the needs of the students, and meets what is expected of them. Teaching effectiveness is a type of classroom exchange between the teacher and the students that leads to the rapid expansion of students' knowledge. It promotes students' engagement in class and increases academic achievements.

Significance of the Study

Due to the rapid explosion of knowledge and significant changes in the subject matter of all disciplines in the field of education, teaching has become a very challenging, complex, and versatile profession today. The student's progress and achievement are strongly influenced by a teacher's competence, sensitivity, commitment, and motivation to the teaching profession. Teaching effectiveness is the cornerstone of learning at all educational levels because effective teaching promotes students' effective learning. However, our country's main problem right now is that the quality of education needs to be improved. As a result of the concern about quality decline, there is a great need for effective teaching and teachers to raise the level of quality teaching. If we use effective teaching strategies with the aid of effective teachers, we can produce high-quality teaching.

Review of Related Literature

The researcher has conducted several studies to examine the effect of demographic variables (gender and type of school) on teaching effectiveness. Babu (2013) revealed that government schools provided an open and nurturing environment to their teachers as compared to private schools, thus resulting in a high level of teaching effectiveness. Islahi & Nasreen (2013) found that married female teachers possessed high teaching effectiveness as compared to married male teachers. Degi & Zangmu (2017) found a significant difference in teaching effectiveness between male and female teachers. Devi & Meena (2018) reported that no significant difference was found in teaching effectiveness regarding their gender and locality.

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

- 1) **Teaching Effectiveness:** Teaching Effectiveness is the ability of a teacher to perform his task of teaching effectively in the classroom. It is a teacher's skill to help learners actualize learning gains in relation to their academic potential.
- 2) **Senior Secondary School Teacher:** Here in the present study, the term 'Senior Secondary School Teachers' means those teachers who teach the students of standard 11th and 12th in different senior secondary schools in West Bengal.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.
- 2) To study the significant difference in teaching effectiveness between male and female senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.
- 3) To study the significant difference in the teaching effectiveness between Govt.-aided and Private senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Hypotheses of the Study

Ho1: There is no significant difference in teaching effectiveness between male and female senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in teaching effectiveness between Govt.- aided and Private senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Methodology of the Study

The researcher used a descriptive survey method in the present study. All the senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district from West Bengal are considered as a population. A sample of 120 senior secondary school teachers was selected through a simple random sampling technique. The researcher used a self-constructed Teaching Effectiveness Scale (2022) to measure the level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers. This scale consists of 32 items under the five dimensions. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability value of the scale is 0.906, and the Split-half reliability value is 0.902. The statistical techniques, i.e., Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and t-test, were used for analyzed the data.

Results and Interpretation

Objective: To study the level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Table 1: Showing the Level of Teaching Effectiveness

Sl. No.	Level of Teaching Effectiveness	Frequency	Percentage
1.	High	20	16.7
2.	Medium	76	63.30
3.	Low	24	20.00
	Total	120	100.00

From table 1, the researcher shows the level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers in the district of Murshidabad, West Bengal. The result indicates that 16.7% of senior secondary school teachers have a high level of teaching effectiveness, 63.30% have a medium, and 20% have a low level of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers in the district of Murshidabad of West Bengal.

Figure: 1 showing the Level of Teaching Effectiveness

Ho1: There is no significant difference in teaching effectiveness between male and female senior

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secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Table 2: Showing the significant difference in Teaching Effectiveness between male and female senior secondary school teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.	Ho.
Male	75	138.76	11.09	-2.45	.016	R
Female	45	143.60	9.30			

*Significant at 0.05 level

Table 2 shows that the t-value is -2.45 and the p-value is .016, smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), which is significant at the 0.05 level. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is a significant difference in teaching effectiveness between male and female senior secondary school teachers in Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Figure 2: showing the significant difference in the level of Teaching Effectiveness between Male and Female senior secondary school teachers

Ho2: There is no significant difference in teaching effectiveness between Govt.-aided and Private senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Table 4: Showing the significant difference in teaching effectiveness between Govt.-aided and Private senior secondary school teachers

Type of School	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.	Ho.
Govt.-aided	65	138.57	11.85	-2.27	.025	R
Private	55	142.95	8.63			

*Significant at 0.05 level

Table 4 shows that the t-value is -2.27, and the p-value is .025, smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$), which is also significant at a 0.05 level of significance. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. It indicates that there is a significant difference in teaching effectiveness between Govt.-aided and Private senior secondary school teachers of Murshidabad district, West Bengal.

Figure 4: Showing the significant difference in teaching effectiveness between Govt.-aided and Private senior secondary school teachers

Major Findings of the Study

The present study found various levels of teaching effectiveness among senior secondary school teachers in the Murshidabad district, West Bengal. This finding coincides with the previous studies conducted by Kiadese (2011), Chowdhury (2014), and Kothawade (2014). The present study revealed that the level of teaching effectiveness differs concerning gender. Female senior secondary school teachers have a high level of teaching effectiveness compared to male senior secondary school teachers. This finding is supported by the studies of Sharadha & Pareswaram (2008), Kothawade (2014), and Dash and Barman (2018). This study also revealed that private senior secondary school teachers have higher teaching effectiveness levels than the Govt.-aided senior secondary school teachers in Murshidabad, West Bengal district. This finding is supported by the study of Devi & Meena (2018) and denied the study by Lata & Tripathi (2020). They revealed that Govt. school teachers have a higher level of teaching effectiveness than private school teachers.

Conclusion

Teaching effectiveness or effective teaching is the cornerstone of learning at all educational levels because effective teaching promotes students' effective learning. The present study found various levels of teaching effectiveness of senior secondary school teachers of the Murshidabad district, West Bengal. This study reveals that female teachers' teaching effectiveness is higher than male teachers. This study also shows that private senior secondary school teachers have higher teaching effectiveness levels than Govt.-aided senior secondary school teachers. However, if teachers are aware of their responsibilities and duties and are accountable to their profession, their teaching effectiveness will enhance students' effective learning and holistic development.

References

- [1] Babu, A. (2013). Organizational climate as a predictor of teacher effectiveness. *European Academic Research*, 1(5), 553-568.
- [2] Chowdhury, S. R. (2014). Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in relation to their Gender, Age, Experience and Qualification. *The Clarion-International Multidisciplinary Journal*, Volume: 3, Issue: 1, 141-148.
- [3] Dash, U., & Barman, P. (2018). Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in the District of Purba Medinipur, West Bengal. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* Volume 21, Issue 7.
- [4] Degi, K., & Zangmu, L. (2017). A Study on Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers of Tawang District, Arunachal Pradesh. *International Education and Research Journal*. E-ISSN No: 2454-9916, Volume: 3 Inter
- [5] Devi, S. & Meena (2018). Teaching Effectiveness of School Teachers in relation to their Attributes. *International Journal of Social Science*. ISSN 2347-3797

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A STUDY OF ICT KNOWLEDGE OF TEACHER EDUCATORS IN RELATION TO THEIR DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

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Abstract

Information and communication technology have affected many facets of human existence in the contemporary era. ICT has also had an impact on teacher education. The present study's objective is to determine the ICT knowledge level of teacher educators in Murshidabad district of West Bengal. This study also identifies the significant differences in ICT knowledge according to gender, locality, and type of college. The researcher used a descriptive research method. A self-constructed questionnaire was used to collect the data. The study included 100 teacher educators from the Murshidabad district of West Bengal. The sample was drawn using a simple random sampling procedure. The present study reveals that 19% of teacher educators have low, 64% have medium, and 17% have high ICT knowledge. This study also shows that there is no significant difference in ICT knowledge according to the gender and type of college of the teacher educators.

Keywords: *Information and Communication Technology, ICT Knowledge, Teacher Educators*

Introduction

Information and communication technology (ICT) has become an indispensable component of human society. Educational institutions are increasingly adopting ICT to allow instructors and students adapt with the twenty-first century expectations on skills and talents. ICT provides educators with the chance to revolutionize teaching and learning. Instructors use various ICT tools to communicate with and engage students in a more meaningful way. ICT allows teachers exploit digital information and share with the whole class to enhance students' digital information (Siddiq et al., 2016). It has significant role in improving teaching competency of the educators (Gudmundsdottir & Hatlevik, 2018). Interaction levels, immediacy, and the opportunity to renew work have all been highlighted as ways in which ICT could increase the diversity of teaching styles employed (Erkan, 2019). It also provides an innovative learning environment in which students build cognitive thinking abilities and learn to explore.

Significance of the Study

The fast growth of technology affects all spheres of life and society, and education is no exception. ICT plays a vital role in the field of teacher education. It provides new possibilities in the teaching-learning process and facilitates teacher interaction with the students. It enables teacher educators to employ ICT software and hardware in the classroom. It improves the teaching skills and professional development of the teacher educators. It replaces the traditional teaching method with the modern method of teaching to improve the teaching-learning process. Good ICT Knowledge of teacher educators would boost higher education's productivity and brighten the student's future. Teacher educators should understand how to utilise technology to augment conventional teaching and how ICT may be introduced into the teaching and learning process to encourage student learning. Therefore, the researcher chooses the present study to know the level of ICT Knowledge of the teacher educators and its impact on the teaching-learning process.

Review of the Related Literature

The researcher had gone through several studies related to ICT. Mailizar and Fan (2020) observed that Indonesian secondary math teachers generally lacked an understanding of ICT and how to use it in the classroom. Hafifah and Sulistyo (2020) assessed ICT literacy of teachers and ICT Integration in ELT in the Indonesian Higher Education and found that more than 60% of teachers had above-average ICT literacy skills and use it in teaching. However, they still had challenges with internet access and ICT training. Saravanan and Nagadeepa (2016) examined the amount of ICT knowledge, utilization, and availability of ICT resources in the classroom environment and found that students studying at city-based institutions had a high degree of ICT knowledge but the ICT awareness level was low even ICT tools were available in class. Hamissi et al. (2012) examined the information literacy and attitude toward knowledge of ICT of dental students and observed that male and female students had same attitude toward knowledge of ICT

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Operational Definition of the Key Terms

- 1) **Information and Communication Technology (ICT):** Information and Communications Technology (ICT) refers to any technology used to gather, store, utilise, or transmit information, including those involving the use of computers or any communications system.
- 2) **ICT Knowledge:** Information and communications technology (ICT) knowledge refers to one's ability to converse with people through various technologies.
- 3) **Teacher Educator:** In the present study, the Teacher Educators are those who work as teachers in the B.Ed. Colleges to teach the B.Ed. trainee.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the level of ICT Knowledge of Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.
- 2) To determine the significant difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.
- 3) To find out the significant difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Hypotheses of the Study

H₀-1: There is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

H₀-2: There is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Methodology of the Study

The researcher used a Descriptive research method and quantitative approach to fulfil the objectives of the current study. The population included Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal and from this 100 Teacher Educators had been selected as sample using simple random sampling technique. A self-constructed "Information and Communication Technology Knowledge Scale" (ICTKS) was used to collect the data for the current study. This scale consisted of 45 items under the seven dimensions. The reliability of the scale is 0.918 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.876 (Guttman Split-Half Coefficient). For data analysis, the researcher calculated Mean, Standard Deviation (SD) and t-test using SPSS (Version 20).

Result and Interpretation

Objective- 1: To study the level of ICT Knowledge of Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Table 1: Level of ICT Knowledge

Level of ICT Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Low	19	19
Medium	64	64
High	17	17
Total	100	100

The above table shows the level of ICT Knowledge of Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal. It indicates that 19% of teacher educators have a low level of ICT Knowledge, 64% have a medium level of ICT Knowledge, and 17% have a high level of ICT Knowledge.

Figure 1: Level of ICT Knowledge

H₀-1: There is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Table 2: ICT Knowledge between Male and Female Teacher Educators

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t- value	Sig.
Male	72	171.47	21.59	1.040	.301
Female	28	166.39	22.77		

NS. (2-tailed)

Table 2 shows that there is no mean difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female teacher educators. The t value = 1.040, ($p=0.301 > 0.05$) indicates that there is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female teacher educators. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 2: ICT Knowledge between Male and Female Teacher Educators

H₀-2: There is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private Teacher Educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Table 3 shows the difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private teacher educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal. The t-value is 1.176, and the p-value is 0.243, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. It indicates that there is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private teacher educators. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: ICT Knowledge between Govt. and Private Teacher Educators

Type of College	N	Mean	S.D	t- value	Sig.
Govt.	11	162.73	27.35	1.176	.243
Private	89	170.96	21.19		

NS. (2-tailed)

Figure 3: ICT Knowledge between Govt. and Private Teacher Educators

Findings of the study

The present study reveals that 19% of teacher educators have a low level of ICT Knowledge, 64% have a medium level of ICT Knowledge, and 17% have a high level of ICT Knowledge. The current study indicates that there is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between male and female teacher educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal. The finding coincides with the previous study conducted by Hamissi et al. (2012). This study also reveals that there is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge between Govt. and private teacher educators of Murshidabad district of West Bengal.

Conclusion

ICT is one of the key contributors to our society's fast evolution. The use of ICT may improve educational quality, broaden learning possibilities, and make education more accessible. The nature of education and the responsibilities of the teacher and student in the teaching-learning process may change as a result. The present study reveals that 19% of teacher educators have low, 64% have medium, and 17% have high ICT Knowledge. This study also shows that there is no significant difference in ICT Knowledge according to the gender and type of college of the teacher educators.

References

- [1] Erkan, A. (2019). Impact of Using Technology on Teacher-Student Communication/Interaction: Improve Students Learning. *World Journal of Education*, 9(4), 30-40.
- [2] Gudmundsdottir, G. B., & Hatlevik, O. E. (2018). Newly qualified teachers' professional digital competence: implications for teacher education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(2), 214-231.
- [3] Hafifah, G. N., & Sulisty, G. H. (2020). Teachers' ICT Literacy and ICT Integration in ELT in the Indonesian Higher Education Setting. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 21(3), 186-198.
- [4] Hamissi, J., Gholami, S. & Hamissi, H. (2012). Evaluation of Information and Communication Technology Knowledge among Undergraduate Dental Students in Iran. *Asian Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 2: 8 (2012) 247– 250, ISSN: 2249-5126.
- [5] Mailizar, M., & Fan, L. (2020). Indonesian Teachers' Knowledge of ICT and the Use of ICT in Secondary Mathematics Teaching. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(1).
- [6] Saravanan, T. & Nagadeepa, N. (2016). A Survey on Applications and Awareness about ICT. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, ISSN: 2277 128X, Volume 6, Issue 8.

THE REFLECTIVE PRACTITIONER AND ACTION RESEARCHER: THE NEW FACE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

National Education policy 2020 has brought in a new hope, a new aspiration towards revolutionizing the educational ethos and backdrop on true lines of creating an environment for holistic development of our children. The promise of the guiding principles mentioned in the policy document are immense but their realization at the grass root level requires massive transformation at the working platform end. There is a complete hierarchy of changes that are required from the curricular framework perspective to subject specific guidelines, perceptual training of school administrators to radical professional training of the prospective teachers. The present paper narrows down from this macroscopic perspective to the microscopic view of a classroom ecosystem, wherein through the tools of reflective practices and action research, the teacher in the classroom acts as the active agent of change, who puts in earnest efforts in providing child centric holistic educational experiences. This inevitably brings us to the immense significance of training teachers to firstly understand this huge responsibility they have on their shoulders, then meticulously train them to organize and plan their classroom experiences designed to foster critical yet creative, individual to group, firm yet flexible skills. Teacher training programmes need to skillfully develop the empowered perspective in teachers that they are the radical instrument of change, then also give them a ground reality check that within organizational, syllabus, assessment and time constraint, the teacher needs to continuously reflect on the best practices possible and through action research try to find her own solutions than waiting for extrinsic solutions to come. Critical review of policy documents, curriculum frameworks, other published literary works and individual reflections as practicing science teacher in a CBSE recognized school paves the way to weave in the spiral of this article.

Keywords: *Reflective teaching, Action Research, Teacher Training, Learner Centered Curriculum*

Introduction

The conventional teaching methodology has the teacher in the Centre, the pivotal agent of authority, the director, the creator, the executor and the assessor (Toh, K. A., 1994). It's been more than two decades of us teacher educators talking about making our curriculum learner centric, using innovative pedagogies, fostering holistic development and bringing the children out of the predominant culture of silence (Elen, J., Clarebout, G., Léonard, R., & Lowyck, J., 2007). If all these principles still lay in the arena of policy perspective and theory mentioned in curriculum but has not transformed into even an initiation of it being a living reality, then as the critical community we need to introspect at the hurdles in execution of the same, and pave the path ahead towards bringing progressive solutions (Null, W., 2016). This paper moves from the arena of policy perspective under the light of National Education Policy 2020 to the broad curriculum framework, from teacher education to the teacher in class. The paper will weave its arguments around the spiral of critical analysis and reflection on treading the progressive path ahead, towards building truly learner centered school education.

Review of Related Literature

The given paper moves through a comprehensive understanding arising from critical study of diverse literary works. This section gives a precise summary of some of the pertinent works studied to build up the theoretical and critical underpinnings of this paper. Central Board of Secondary Education, Secondary Curriculum Classes IX-X for session 2022-23. Presents a comprehensive description of the objectives, principles, curricular areas, assessment scheme, concepts of art integration, health and physical education for classes IX and X. Thompson, S., & Thompson, N. (2022) is a handbook for the reflective practitioner who bases her work on critical observations and analysis continuum. Gupta, B. L., & Choubey, A. K. (2021) has discussed in detail the guidelines for sustenance of higher education institutions after guidelines issued by NEP. Sharma, K. (2021) elaborates on how through school experiences value inculcation can be successfully done, amidst challenges and constraints. Kumar, A. (2021) has talked about the immense revolutionary power that NEP 2020 has in creating a new version of India altogether. A well researched out piece that articulates a beautiful vision of India ahead with educational

reforms. Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020) presents a critical reflective analysis of of NEP 2020 towards how it aims to achieve its goals, the path ahead – promises and challenges. Al-Balushi, S. M., Ambusaidi, A. K., Al-Balushi, K. A., Al-Hajri, F. H., & Al-Sinani, M. S. (2020) presents contrasting approaches i.e. student centred versus teacher centred especially in context of a science classroom where constructivism and learning by doing form the basic premise. National Education Policy 2020 is the elaborate policy document which in detail deals with the issues at unrest in school education, higher education, other area of concern and how they can be effectively dealt with. Govinda, R. (2020) leads through a critical examination of NEP as a policy document aiming at bringing radical transformations in the education ethos and culture of our country. Kalyani, P. (2020) presents a comprehensive insight into the vision of New India under the light of NEP by carefully analysing the locatedness of the different stake holders in this vision. Study of the above mentioned literary works and the others listed in references, helped the researcher identify some pertinent themes, under which the remain part of the paper is segregated.

The New Education Policy 2020: A Ray of Hope

New Education Policy 2020, published by the Ministry of Human Resource and development, Government of India has woven its guiding principles spun around the quintessential tenet of ensuring holistic development of children at its core. Undeniably, the new age education relies on the pillars of active child participation, learner centeredness, individualised curriculum, flexibility in terms of content to be studied, value inculcation, problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, problem solving skills and active citizenship (Nan-Zhao, Z., 2005). The basic tenet in here is that all these qualities are not achieved inherently on attainment of adulthood, rather they are inculcated over the experiences of children especially in the school years in its teaching learning environment (Sharma, K., 2021). The importance of inculcation of these skills, values and qualities is beyond debate but the question in here is how to achieve the same at the grass root level (Redish, M. H., & Finnerty, K., 2002). NEP 2020 boldly accepts that basic numeracy and literacy are the major challenges we are facing in context of minimal standards of learning. It has also accepted that the bulk of syllabus and the elaborate system of summative examinations has encaged our education in the prevalent ‘coaching culture’ system (Kalyani, P., 2020). The document takes cognisance of the fact that to bring the essence of learning back to the classroom we need to reduce the bulky syllabus, focus on teaching of core concepts only and testing of the same via series of small formative assessments, so that there is ample time and scope for inculcation of child participatory and investigatory projects in the classroom (Govinda, R., 2020). Second bold and necessary acceptance of NEP is the alarming state of teacher education in our country. The document accepts a significantly large number of teacher education institutions are not providing the necessary teacher training rather are just acting as organisation to render the degrees for employability (Gupta, B. L., & Choubey, A. K., 2021). This has had a huge derogatory impact on the quality of school education in our country and is one of the major impediment towards non-actualisation of the celebrated principles of learner centred education and holistic development of children (Kumar, A., 2021). The document asserts the necessary changes desired in this segment in terms of new integrated formal degree courses that will give the professional training in terms of both perspective development and skills required in the class front. Inevitably a radical transformation in teacher education is required to develop the skills but the components of the teacher training programme also need to be carefully reflected on (Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S., 2020). Even though the NEP has emphasized on the inculcation of true educational principles in the teacher trainees, the major test of the same lies in the real school scenario. For this now an extensive ‘School Experience programme’ is an inevitable component of the training programme (Panditrao, M. M., & Panditrao, M. M., 2020). But when the teacher trainee enters into the real school set up, the educational world around her may or may not be in sync with what has been taught (Menon, S., 2020). Organisational and institutional goals are majorly consumerist and are based on some scalar parameters of completion of syllabus, the marks scored by students in examination, evidences of the work in form of written assignments, photographs of assessments and so on. The teacher on job finds herself enclutched in these new goals that judge her professional skills and forms the basis of sustained employability. The route, the path towards attaining the mentioned goals in policy document needs to overcome these real challenges of the teachers working at the ground level.

The Document: Case of CBSE School Curriculum

The researcher and writer of this article has over a decade of experience of teaching Science at Secondary level in a CBSE recognised school in Delhi and this segment is based on her reflections and critical analysis during her journey from the ideological domains of teacher training institute to the realistic school employment scenario. For any teacher in the conventional school set up, the guiding document of curriculum is issued by the

board, school is affiliated with. The school is bound to comply and strictly follow the prescribed curriculum, as any deviation from the same may lead to disciplinary actions and even cancelling the recognition of the school. Also, since the parents also expect their child to appear in the public examinations being organised by the board and score well for further admissions and adding meritorious component to their curriculum vitae, following the prescribed curriculum is the stringent as well as the expected norm. In the real sense, the curriculum document let's say the one issued by CBSE is a very strong tool in the hands of the curriculum framers who wish to give in clear guidelines for ensuring its compliance across all organisations. The curriculum framework is a very broad document, that gives in the objectives, theoretical background, principles to be achieved in a very general and broad sense. Then at the second level, let's say in the Secondary school Curriculum, CBSE has divided the document in two parts first are the chapters to be covered compulsorily and second is the scheme of examination that has to be uniformly followed across all institutions. Since these two only form the content matter of the subject specific document, the entire focus of the teacher also revolves around the completion of the chapters – its diverse topics and subtopics with the primary aim of training the children to score well in the summative examinations. The marks obtained in these examinations is taken as a measure of the success attributed to the teaching and learning done throughout the year. The conventional outlook analyses the teacher based on the marks obtained by the students in the examination. So now it becomes relevant to analyse the content of the question paper, issued by the board as final examination paper, which is the prime focus of teaching learning across the session. The paper involves factual, knowledge based and descriptive answers which do require learning and revision, few competency and case based questions have been included but the bulk of the syllabus (full textbook) for year end examination, makes all the teaching learning energy primarily directed towards this examination. NEP as discussed in the previous section, has talked about understanding of only core concepts (lessen the burden of syllabus) and testing of core concepts only (that can be understood in the course of normal classroom transactions) via the means of an easy question paper. The purpose of this approach is not to minimise the content of the syllabus and to degrade the difficulty level of the question paper, but it is to free rather empower the teacher from the constraints of burdening syllabus and exhaustive examinations. Now we come back to the quintessential question that then what is the aim of this policy directive? The aim is to create provision for true inculcation of critical thinking, creative thinking, problem solving and diverse other skills, which require in time and flexibility, as it moves with the dynamic response, progress and suitedness of each child with the activity at par. The other major challenge in development of individualised progressive curriculums for children for identifying their unique innate potential, for their holistic development is class strength (Viennet, R., & Pont, B., 2017). With around 40 students in an average Indian classroom, making multiple observations per student, designing individual activities as per their needs and interest, redesigning as per the progress, requires in time, which has been suitably recognised by NEP and is a revolutionary change to initiate progress in the right direction of providing holistic development to our children. A policy document may give the right direction, but school doesn't derive its curriculum directly from the policy document, it waits for the curricular guidelines to come in from the board and then that curriculum is strictly followed in. Since NEP 2020, deletion in syllabus was observed by CBSE but due to the expansive, elaborate and stringent question paper pattern, the focus still was on preparing for the final board examination. The wait of the teacher still lies in the coming of the new curriculum framework (after NCF 2005), that will empower the teacher to truly create joyful, engaging, individualised, flexible and holistic teaching learning environment for children. The struggle of the teacher lies in creating the best of the learning opportunities for children (to whatever extent possible) within the working constraints of lack of continuity between the working variables of policy and curriculum document for the teacher at grass root level.

The Reflective Practitioner: The New Age Teacher

The new age teacher has to be trained into being a thinking, reflective, problem solving, positive and happy individual (Johns, C., 2009). Policies and curriculums are beyond the jurisdiction or control of the teacher, but yes how she aims to create the ecosystem of her classroom is within her work arena. Teachers have to be trained in thinking and putting up their best effort in creating beautiful learning spaces for the children. Teachers have to be trained to reflect, to observe, to critically analyse the situation and come up with the best classroom solutions (Adler, S., 1991). Values are not taught, rather they are caught, so when we create in such opportunities for children to lead, to think, to explore, to plan, to design, to implement, to execute, to assess, to reflect and based on reflection come back to the same stage of planning, well than before (Schön, D. A., 2017). This same continuum of reflection is not only a learning tool used by the children but actually forms a quintessential reflective cycle of the teacher, who has to continuously introspect on the direction in which the progress is moving and how it can be further strengthened. Maintaining reflective journals, reflective diaries, portfolios, anecdotal

record, case studies will inevitably be useful in the reflective planning and implementation process, especially in higher class strengths (Copeland, W. D., Birmingham, C., de la Cruz, E., & Lewin, B., 1993). Reflection is an art, and it comes with a foundational training in philosophical, historical and psychological perspectives in education. The knowledge of the policy documents and the curricular theories, further brings the teacher to a much informed wise reflection as against a teacher not having a formal training in education (Thompson, S., & Thompson, N., 2022). Reflective analysis can be based on individual observations, personalised interaction with students, small groups, bigger groups, parents and co-teachers. Teacher needs to be on a curious, attentive, caring and concerned mode to understand the innate potential of every child, bringing their inner qualities to the forefront, so that activities and specific tasks can be designed to further polish and develop these skills (Plack, M. M., & Greenberg, L., 2005).

Teacher as Action Researcher: The Empowered Tool Towards Sustained Professional Development

Reflective teaching learning practices bring us to an inevitable positioning of teacher as an action researcher. Classroom is the laboratory of testing our pedagogical plan, of validating of thinking of how to make it better day by day. To be at par with the dynamic children, the teacher needs to constantly invent-reinvent her lesson plans, teaching aids, teaching methodologies, see whether the discourse went in the planned direction or not (Stringer, E. T., 2008). Since we are dealing with dynamic interests, energies, abilities, aptitudes, skills and attitudes of children, our teaching learning methodologies also need to have the continuous element of dynamism to keep the energies of the children concentrated voluntarily in the classroom learning processes (Efron, S. E., & Ravid, R., 2019). The teacher education programmes inevitably teaches the make organised lesson plans, cull out the objectives, select the methodology and assess the learning, but the added element over a structured lesson plan is the element of reflection which in its cycle of feedback and new inclusions makes the teacher a live researcher in the classroom (Nolen, A. L., & Putten, J. V., 2007). Teacher training programmes needs to instil this necessary training in the teachers of being action researchers, the policy directives may vary, the curricular guidelines may be diverse with every passing session but via the agency of reflective teaching and action research, the new age teacher is fully equipped, empowered in her own capabilities to put in her earnest efforts committed to progress of children alone (Tran, T. T. H., 2009). To build up individualised curricular plans, constant revision, updation and validating its suitability in required (Cardno, C., 2003).

The Three 'D' Perspective: The Last Post

Fostering children to become active, productive, problem solving and contributing citizens of the state, to instil in them the value of initiating participation in issues of concern and making efforts to make the world a better place to be in; fostering the values of mutual respect, co-operation and progress, is primarily rooted in a democratic classroom set up (Subba, D., 2014). The teacher education needs to ensure that the legacy of traditional schooling i.e. the culture of silence is discontinued and the teacher trainees move out with the culture of teacher stepping back and letting the children lead from the front, right from designing to execution to assessment and then re-designing of curricular experiences (Alshurman, M., 2015). Teacher as the facilitator, teacher as the reflective practitioner, teacher as the action researcher truly is the new face of teacher education in the realms of the first 'D' i.e. democratisation of education. The second 'D' signifies the developmental perspective, in which through agency of joint reflection and joint action research with children, we instil the developmental opportunities of critical thinking, creativity, problem solving life skills which further brings us to the new shore of holistic development as the prime focus of teacher education programme (Early, D. M., Maxwell, K. L., Burchinal, M., Alva, S., Bender, R. H., Bryant, D & Zill, N. (2007). The third 'D' signifies the 'Dialogic perspective' (Wegerif, R., 2019). Joint reflection and joint action research, the amalgamation of teacher and student, which promotes dialogicity, a culture of mutual respect and a society of decent communication. In this perspective, we do not ascertain that we should follow whatever children have to say but at least explain to them why a particular option has been selected and not the other, that the child may be preferred. Dynamism is the inevitable component at the level of society, economics, politics, history, geography, psychology, sociology which inevitable brings change in educational aspirations and desired learning outcomes. The new age teacher also needs to keep herself updated, and continuously on the learning path, and the tools of reflection and action research undeniably add to her dynamic learning ethos, making her empowered and equipped to truly manifest the principles of NEP 2020 into a living reality.

References

- [1] Adler, S. (1991). The reflective practitioner and the curriculum of teacher education. *Journal of Education*

- for teaching, 17(2), 139-150.
- [2] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards achieving its objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 19-41.
- [3] Al-Balushi, S. M., Ambusaidi, A. K., Al-Balushi, K. A., Al-Hajri, F. H., & Al-Sinani, M. S. (2020). Student-centred and teacher-centred science classrooms as visualized by science teachers and their supervisors. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 89, 103014.
- [4] Alshurman, M. (2015). Democratic education and administration. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 861-869.
- [5] Cardno, C. (2003). *Action Research: A Developmental Approach*. New Zealand Council for Educational Research, PO Box 3237, Wellington, New Zealand.
- [6] Copeland, W. D., Birmingham, C., de la Cruz, E., & Lewin, B. (1993). The reflective practitioner in teaching: Toward a research agenda. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 9(4), 347-359.
- [7] Cheetham, G., & Chivers, G. (1998). The reflective (and competent) practitioner: a model of professional competence which seeks to harmonise the reflective practitioner and competence-based approaches. *Journal of European industrial training*.
- [8] Early, D. M., Maxwell, K. L., Burchinal, M., Alva, S., Bender, R. H., Bryant, D., ... & Zill, N. (2007). Teachers' education, classroom quality, and young children's academic skills: Results from seven studies of preschool programs. *Child development*, 78(2), 558-580.
- [9] Efron, S. E., & Ravid, R. (2019). *Action research in education: A practical guide*. Guilford Publications.
- [10] Elen, J., Clarebout, G., Léonard, R., & Lowyck, J. (2007). Student-centred and teacher-centred learning environments: What students think. *Teaching in higher education*, 12(1), 105-117.
- [11] Govinda, R. (2020). NEP 2020: A critical examination. 603-607
- [12] Gupta, B. L., & Choubey, A. K. (2021). Higher education institutions—some guidelines for obtaining and sustaining autonomy in the context of NEP 2020. *Higher Education*, 9(1).
- [13] Hine, G. S. (2013). The importance of action research in teacher education programs. *Issues in Educational research*, 23(2), 151-163.
- [14] Johns, C. (2009). *Becoming a reflective practitioner*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [15] Kalyani, P. (2020). An empirical study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with special reference to the future of Indian education system and its effects on the Stakeholders. *Journal of Management Engineering and Information Technology*, 7(5), 1-17.
- [16] Kumar, A. (2021). *New education policy (NEP) 2020: A roadmap for India 2.0*. University of South Florida M3 Center Publishing, 3(2021), 36.
- [17] Menon, S. (2020). NEP 2020: Some Searching Questions. 599-602
- [18] Nan-Zhao, Z. (2005). Four 'pillars of learning' for the reorientation and reorganization of curriculum: Reflections and discussions. *International Bureau of Education-UNESCO*.
- [19] Nolen, A. L., & Putten, J. V. (2007). Action research in education: Addressing gaps in ethical principles and practices. *Educational researcher*, 36(7), 401-407.
- [20] Null, W. (2016). *Curriculum: From theory to practice*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- [21] Panditrao, M. M., & Panditrao, M. M. (2020). National Education Policy 2020: What is in it for a student, a parent, a teacher, or us, as a Higher Education Institution/University?. *Adesh University Journal of Medical Sciences & Research*, 2(2), 70-79.
- [22] Plack, M. M., & Greenberg, L. (2005). The reflective practitioner: reaching for excellence in practice. *Pediatrics-English Edition*, 116(6), 1546-1552.
- [23] Redish, M. H., & Finnerty, K. (2002). What Did You Learn in School Today-Free Speech, Values Inculcation, and the Democratic-Educational Paradox. *Cornell L. Rev.*, 88, 62.

EFFECT OF FARTLEK TRAINING ON SELECTED MOTOR FITNESS VARIABLE AMONG HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of fartlek training on selected motor fitness variable among hockey players. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty hockey players were selected from Alagappa University, Karaikudi Tamilnadu, India during the year 2022. The subject's age ranges from 18 to 25 years. The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups consists of 15 subjects each namely experimental group and control group. The experimental group under went a Fartlek Training programme for six weeks. The control group was not taking part in any training during the course of the study. Speed was taken as criterion variable in this study. The selected subjects were tested on speed was measured through 50 yards dash. Pre-test was taken before the training period and post- test was measured immediately after the six week training period. Statistical technique 't' ratio was used to analyse the means of the pre-test and post test data of experimental group and control group. The results revealed that there was a significant difference found on the criterion variable. The difference is found due to Fartlek Training given to the experimental group on speed when compared to control group.

Keywords: *Fartlek Training, Speed and 'T' ratio.*

Introduction

Fartlek training or speed play was created by Gosta Roamer of Sweden. The definition of Fartlek is a endurance exercise system which means it is to build, restore or maintain a person's body condition so that it is very good for all sports branches especially sports that require endurance. Fartlek training combines aerobic demands with continuous movement with speed intervals, the method of Fartlek training is a very enjoyable exercise and aims to increase the strength and capacity of aerobic athletes (Jones, 2016).

Research Methodology

Selection of Subjects: The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Fartlek training on speed ability among hockey players. To achieve this purpose of the study, hockey players were selected as subjects at random. The age of the subjects were ranged from 18 to 25 years. **Election of variable:** independent variable - fartlek training. dependent variable – speed. **Experimental design and implementation:** the selected subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each, such as a fartlek training group (experimental group) and control group. the experimental group underwent fartlek training for five days per week for six weeks. control group, which they did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical activities as per their curriculum. the following motor fitness variable namely speed was selected as criterion variable. all the subjects of two groups were tested on selected criterion variable speed was measured through 50 yards dash at prior to and immediately after the training programme. **Statistical Technique:** The 't' test was used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively. **Level of Significance:** The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent 't' test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

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Table: 1 Analysis Of T-Ratio For The Pre And Post Tests Of Experimental And Control Group On Speed

Variables	Group	Standard Deviation		SdError	
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Speed	ControlGroup	0.359	0.358	0.093	0.092
	ExperimentalGroup	0.355	0.373	0.091	0.096

Table2

Variables	Group	Mean		Degree of freedom	't' ratio
		Pre	Post		
Speed	ControlGroup	7.28	7.29	14	0.64
	ExperimentalGroup	7.30	7.08	14	5.59*

*Significance at .05 level of confidence.

The Table-I and II shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the controlgroup on speed were 7.28 and 7.29 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.64, since theobtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.14 for the significant at 0.05level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group on speed were 7.30 and 7.08 respectively.The obtained 't' ratio was 5.59* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.14 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to best Statistically significant. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between control group and experimental group in speed. It may be concluded from the result of the study that experimental group improved in speed due to six weeks of Fartlek training.

Figure-1 Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of Experimental and Control Group on Speed

Discussions on Findings

The result of the study indicates that the experimental group, namely Fartlek training group had significantly improved the selected dependent variable, namely speed, when compared to the control group. It is also found that the improvement caused by Fartlek training when compared to the control group.

Conclusion

On the basis of the results obtained the following conclusions are drawn, there was a significant difference between experimental and control group on speed after the training period, a significant improvement in speed.

References

- [1] Balamuralikrishnan R and Yoga P. (2018). Effect of varied intensity of aerobic training on Self Esteem. International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health. 5(2), pp.284-285.
- [2] James Rathinaraj S. and Yoga P. (2018). Structured resistance training on Vo2 Max. International Journal of Physical Education Sports and Health. 5(2), pp.286-287.
- [3] Alaguraja K. and Yoga P. (2018). Effect of core stability training on dynamic strength among college male students. International Journal of Yogic Human Movement and Sports Sciences. 3(2), pp. 436-437.

EFFECT OF SURYANAMASKAR ON SELECTED PHYSIOLOGICAL VARIABLE AMONG AVERAGE FITNESS SCHOOL BOYS

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Abstract

To achieve the purpose of Random group experimental design, 30 school boys were selected randomly from Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu by using Random sampling method between 14 and 20 years of age. The subjects were divided into two groups of 15 subjects each. Experimental group was taken suryanamaskar training for 12 weeks, five day a week for maximum 40 minutes. The control group was not taken any practices but in active rest. The pre-test and post-test were conducted before and after the training for the experimental group and control group on the dependent variables of BMI and diastolic blood pressure. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to find out the significant differences among the groups. The result of the study proved that Body mass index (BMI) and diastolic blood pressure are in balanced due to suryanamaskar among average fitness school boys. Hence the hypothesis was accepted at 0.05 level of confidence. It is concluded that suryanamaskar helped to balance the BMI and diastolic blood pressure among average fitness school boys.

Keywords: *Suryanamaskar, average fitness school boys, Body mass index (BMI)*

Introduction

Discovering and promoting ways that improve adolescents' physiological fitness has been a recurrent concern in the field of health. Adolescence, as a period of transition, is highly prone to have both physical and mental health risks and unhealthy body pattern. Thus, it is the right time to promote healthy practices to prevent problems of health and behaviour in adulthood. As, International Association for the Study of Obesity (IASO) and International Obesity Task Force (IOTF) reckon that 200 million school children worldwide are either overweight or obese. The prevalence of obesity among 5-to 19-year-old Indian children, ranged between 3.6 and 11.7%. It is predicted that by 2025 there will be 17 million obese children in India. Urbanization is the single most important factor linked to obesity in India. Epigenetic, dietary, familial, psychosocial, parental education and parental occupation are other important factors. About 50% of obese children will become obese adults. Yoga provides practical solutions for Physical health, we anticipated that exposure to it should improve Physiological fitness among average fitness school boys.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to find out whether there would be any significant difference on selected Physiological variables such as Body mass index(BMI) and Diastolic blood pressure due to Suryanamaskar on among average fitness school boys.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Suryanamaskar on selected Physiological variables such as Body mass index(BMI) and Diastolic blood pressure among average fitness school boys.

Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences due to the Suryanamaskar on selected Bio Chemical and Physiological variables such as Body mass index(BMI) and Diastolic blood pressure among average fitness school boys than the control group.

Delimitations

The study was delimited to only on average fitness school boys between 14 and 20 years of age. The study was delimited to school boys at Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu only. The independent variable was selected suryanamaskar only. The dependent variables were restricted to Body mass index(BMI) and Diastolic blood pressure only.

Limitations

Changing life style conditions, body structure, occupation and other environmental factors were not taken

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into consideration. Climate conditions and diet patterns were not considered. The other ways of treatment underwent by the subjects were not taken into account. Socio-economic conditions were considered as limitations.

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study, 30 school boys studying in Kannur district, kerala at the age of the subjects was ranged from 14 to 19 years. The subjects were divided into an experimental group and control group of 15 subjects each. The Experimental Group imparted training for 12 weeks, five days a week for a maximum of one hour in the morning. The control group in active rest. The pre-test and post-test were conducted before and after the training for two groups and the scores on Bio Chemical and psychological factors are measured. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to find out the significant differences among the groups.

Results & Discussions

The data pertaining to the variables collected from two groups before and after the training period were statistically analysed by using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant difference and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Table I: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Variance of Body Mass Index (BMI) of Experimental and Control Group

Test	Experimental Group	Control Group	F Ratio
Pre test	26.87	27.02	0.08
Post test	21.15	27.02	20.48*
Adjusted	31.30	16.87	-0.01*

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. (Table F ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 1 and 28 (df) =4.2, 1 and 27(df) = 4.21)

Figure I: Bar Diagram Showing Adjusted Post-Test Values of Control Group and Experimental Group on Body Mass Index (BMI) IN (kg/ m²)

The obtained F ratio on pre test scores 0.08 was lesser than the required F value of 4.2 to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence. This proved that there was no significant difference between the groups in pre-test and the randomization at the pre-test was equal. The post test scores analysis proved that there was significant difference between the groups, as obtained F value 0.08 was greater than the required F value of 4.2. The pre- test, post- test and adjusted post-test mean values of Yogic Practices group and the Control Group on memory were

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graphically presented in Figure I.

Table II: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Variance of Diastolic Blood Pressure of Experimental and Control Group(mm/Hg)

Test	Experimental Group	Control Group	F Ratio
Pre test	92.00	93.40	0.54
Post test	81.13	94.00	76.62*
Adjusted	81.60	93.53	243.29*

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. (Table F ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 1 and 28 (df) =4.2, 1 and 27(df) = 4.21)

Figure II: Bar Diagram Showing Adjusted Post-Test Values of Control Group and Experimental Group on Diastolic Blood Pressure(mmHg)

Discussion on Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on Body mass index and Diastolic Blood Pressure among average fitness school boys due to Suryanamaskar than the Control Group. The results in the tables proved that yogic practices decreased the Body mass index and Diastolic Blood Pressure significantly among average fitness school boys at 0.05 level of confidence.

Conclusion

It was concluded that Suryanamaskar decreased both Body mass index(BMI) and Diastolic blood pressure among average fitness school boys. Hence, Suryanamaskar is beneficial to average fitness school boys.

References

- [1] <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- [2] Devasena, I., & Narhare, P. (2011). Effect of yoga on heart rate and blood pressure and its clinical significance. *Int J Biol Med Res*, 2(3), 750-3.
- [3] Bhumbak, Ravinder. (2014). A comparative study of physical fitness of male yoga and gymnastic players of Hisar distt. *International Journal of Physical Education Sports Management and Yogic*

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICE ON SELECTED MOTOR FITNESS VARIABLE AMONG COLLEGE PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of Yogi Practice on selected Motor Fitness Variable Among College Players. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty hockey players were selected from Alagappa University, Karaikudi Tamilnadu, India during the year 2022. The subject's age ranges from 18 to 25 years. The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups consisting of 15 subjects each namely experimental group and control group. The experimental group underwent a Yogi Practice programme for six weeks. The control group was not taking part in training during the course of the study. Agility was taken as the criterion variable in this study. The selected subjects were tested on Agility which was measured through T- Shuttle run. Pre-test was taken before the training period and post-test was measured immediately after the six-week training period. Statistical technique 't' ratio was used to analyse the means of the pre-test and post-test data of experimental group and control group. The results revealed that there was a significant difference found on the criterion variable. The difference is found due to Yogi Practice given to the experimental group on speed when compared to control group.

Keywords: *Yogi Practice, Agility and 't' ratio.*

Introduction

Yoga is universally benefiting all people of all ages. The study of Yoga is fascinating to those with a philosophical mind and is defined as the silencing of the mind's activities which lead to complete realization of the intrinsic nature of the Supreme Being. It is a practical holistic philosophy designed to bring about profound state as well as an integral subject, which takes into consideration man as a whole. The aim of Yoga is to devise ways and means of helping the better emotional and intellectual concentration. Yoga means the union or communication or unity with our inner being. 'Asana' means a state of being in which we can remain steady, calm, quiet and comfortable with our physical body and mind.

Research Methodology

Selection of subjects: The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Yogi Practice on Agility among College players. To achieve this purpose of the study College players were selected as subjects at random. The age of the subjects was ranged from 18 to 25 years. Independent variable: yogi practice, dependent variable – agility.

Experimental Design and Implementation

The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each, such as a Yogi Practice group (Experimental Group) and control group. The experimental group underwent Yogi Practice for five days per week for six weeks. Control group, which they did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical activities as per their curriculum. The following motor fitness variable namely Agility was selected as the criterion variable. All the subject groups were tested on selected criterion variable Agility which was measured through T- Shuttle run at prior to and immediately after the training programme. Statistical Technique: The 'T' test was used to analyse the significant differences, if any, between the groups respectively. Level of Significance: The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered appropriate.

Analysis of the Data

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent 't' test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

Table-1 Analysis of 't'- ratio the pre and post-test for control and experimental group on Agility

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Variables	Group	Mean		SD		Sd Error	df	't' ratio
		pre	post	pre	post			
Agility	Control	13.19	13.17	1.12	1.14	0.03	14	0.81
	Experimental	13.18	12.54	0.72	0.65	0.11		5.80*

*Significance at .05 level of confidence.

The Table-I shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the control group on Agility were 13.19 and 13.17 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.81, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.15 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group on Agility were 13.18 and 12.54 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 5.80* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.15 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between control group and experimental group in Agility. It may be concluded from the result of the study that experimental group improved in Agility due to six weeks of Yogi Practice.

Figure-1 bar diagram showing the pre and post mean values of experimental and control group on agility

Discussions on findings

The result of the study indicates that the experimental group, namely Yogi Practice group had significantly improved the selected dependent variable, namely Agility, when compared to the control group. It is also found that the improvement caused by Yogi Practice when compared to the control group.

Conclusion

On the basis of the results obtained the following conclusions are drawn, there was a significant difference between experimental and control group on Agility after the training period and a significant improvement in Agility. However the improvement was in favor of experimental group due to six weeks of Yogi Practice.

References

- [1] Ray, U.S., et.al. (2001) "Effect of yogic exercises on physical and mental health of young Fellowship course trainees" *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 45:1, p.37-53.
- [2] Doijad, V. P., Kamble, P., & Surdi, A. D. (2013). Effect of Yogic Exercises on Aerobic Capacity (Vo₂ Max). *International Journal of Physiology*, 1(2), 47-50
- [3] Baechle Thomas R & Earle Roger W. 2008 *Essentials of strength training and conditioning*, Third Edition. Human Kinetics. United States of America.
- [4] Barth Katrin & Bosing Lothar. 2010. *Trainig basketball*. Meyer & Meyer Sports. (Uk) Ltd.

INTEGRATION OF YOGA IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Yoga is considered an important medical technique for developing the physical and mental functioning of an individual. It refers to the system of practices that help to control the mind, body, and soul. It is a holistic path that leads to a sense of peace and well-being. Through different poses (asanas), breathing technique (pranayama), and meditation (dhyana), yoga makes the practitioner aware of his inner self. It includes cultivation of correct attitudes and reconditioning of the neuromuscular systems. Yoga helps the whole body to enable it to withstand greater stress and strain. It proposes healthy diet and encourages the natural process of elimination, whenever it is necessary. Yoga aims at an integrated and harmonious development of all the potentialities of human beings. Several studies have shown that the practice of yoga has a definite role in the promotion of positive health, including mental health.

Keywords: *Yoga, Asanas, Pranayama, Dhyana, Well Being, Positive Health and Mental Health*

Introduction

Yoga is the art and science of living in harmony with one's nature. The practices of yoga enable us to achieve optimum physical health and a mind free from stress, anxiety and the negative effects of tension. They enable us to improve the quality of our mind so we have greater clarity, concentration and memory. Yogic practices are designed to awaken the dormant potential within, which leads to a more balanced and harmonious life. In this way, yoga becomes a path of self-discovery and self-knowledge. First we become more aware of the physical body. This leads to an understanding of how our mind works and how it influences our body and personality. We observe and understand how we think and learn why we have certain attitudes and reactions by discovering the role that emotions play in our life. We also get in touch with the psychic personality lying dormant in the unconscious mind and come into closer contact with our true Self. As we understand more about ourselves, we understand more about how we relate to one another. Awareness leads to understanding, which leads to the ability to be more in control of life. We learn to know when it is right to accept something and when to make the effort to change something. This ability comes through an increase in discrimination, viveka, and non-attachment, vairagya. As we acquire these qualities we find we have more confidence and more self-esteem.

Yoga

Yoga is a noninvasive, cost-effective, and safe intervention among complementary and alternative medicine which is known to have a positive impact on psychological problems. Yoga is one of the alternatives and complementary medicine interventions, which is noninvasive, safe, as well as cost-effective. It has found to be effective in many clinical health conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, asthma, Parkinson's disease, Colgrove et al, (2012). as well as psychological problems such as anxiety Dhansoia , (2015) and depression Woolery(2004).

In addition, research on the practice of yoga – a non-competitive, physical exercise (asana) combined with breathing (pranayama) and meditation techniques (Sengupta, 2012) – indicates that practicing yoga is associated with improved psychological well-being Shapiro and Cline, 2004; Kiecolt-Glaser et al., 2010) and positive self-esteem (Sethi et al., 2013). Practicing yoga postures improves vagal tone increasing bodily energetic resources (Wilhelm et al., 2004; Patil et al., 2013).

Yoga and Health

According to a case study, it was explained that, In 1956, when we started the International Yoga Fellowship, there was ignorance and misunderstanding of yoga everywhere. When I was on my first world tour in 1968–69, I found that it was very difficult for people to understand exactly what yoga meant. Some had vague and incomplete information and thought yoga was a kind of magic or psychic feat. They were not able to understand or place yoga in the scheme of their lives. So we started training sannyasins and sending them all over the world in order to show people what yoga meant. I have been all over the world, not once, but many times, and I have found that everywhere people are looking for illumination. The physical, mental and spiritual problems confronting people of this modern civilisation are innumerable. They are beyond the knowledge of doctors and the control of the government. They are beyond the mental hospitals which will never be able to save humanity. Therefore, in 1963 I established the Bihar School of Yoga. At that time I did not have a single disciple. Now I have yoga centres

all over the world, not because I am a good organiser, but because the principles and practices of yoga are scientifically based. They have already been well tested by the rishis and munis in our land for thousands of years. More interesting, however, is the series of scientific evaluations of yoga which have developed in recent years. Scientists and doctors all over the world are now trying to understand how and why yoga has such a great influence on the human body and mind. Research conducted in the USSR, Poland, France, England, America, Australia and in India also has proved beyond any doubt that the practices of yoga are a scientific process by which physical and mental diseases can be overcome. Yoga is not merely to tone up the body or reduce fat. Now scientists are conducting research into the influence of yogic practices on the brain wave patterns. Today yoga can accept the challenge of the modern scientists who started yogic research with doubt and scepticism, but were soon fantastically impressed by the direct correlations they found between science and yoga. Now yogic research is being carried out in many countries around the world.

Yoga and Modern Education

Integration of Yoga in Modern Education

Yoga is a science of man in depths, is the science of conscious evolution or the science of human possibilities. The modern education is based on science and technology in which some of the best qualities are tending to disappear. Due to modern education productivity, creativity and resources are increasing but on the other hand the man is on the verge of losing moral, religious, cultural and social values which are the most important integral parts of education system. Due to modernization man is not getting peace of mind, becoming violent, aggressive as well as physical and mental disorders are increasing. The reason behind these events is the man's disturbed awareness created due to the disintegration of physique, mind, intellect and spirit. In this context yoga is to be integrated in modern education because yoga has the complete message for humanity, human body human mind and for human spirit as stated by Swami Kunalayandaji. The meaning of integration of yoga in modern education is the harmonization of aims and objects of traditional and spiritual values with the values of science and technology to recognize man as a 'whole man'.

Aspects of Yoga to be Integrated in Modern Education

Modern education is disintegrated due to the lack of harmony between the body, mind, intellect and spirit which are the components of a whole man. To bring a wholeness in man the human sciences like biology, physiology, psychology and sociology help to bring the harmony between the above described four components. In this case yoga helps the man and the eight limbs or aspects of yoga described by Maharshi patanjali will help to integrate body, mind, intellect and spirit.

Extent of Yoga to be Integrated in Modern Education

Modern man is at his best when he is dealing with analysis – his recent education has all tended in that direction. But he runs away from the realities when he comes to synthesis. He seems to have lost the secret of it because the modern education has left it out. Analysis is man's strong point, synthesis his weak one. It is very easy to break a thing up into parts and to study each part in separation but it is rather difficult to put the parts together again. Thus the wholeness or the wholeness seems to be baffled. The division between material thing and the spiritual thing is the result of analysis. The yoga education helps to keep a balance between the analytical and synthetic faculties of a man. It also helps to emancipate a man from all restraints and gives the power of self-expression and self-realization.

Amount of Time to be Allowed to Yoga in Modern Education

Actually speaking yoga is a long journey to achieve the final stage – Kaivalya. We want quick results and also want to get immediate cure; which is rather impossible in yoga. Another thing is the nature of motivation or way in which the knowledge of yoga is to be utilized. Presently we want an integrated personality in which the person's physical, mental and emotional components fit together so that his behaviour becomes normal. A young healthy individual after attaining proper maturity has to do Yagabhyas daily for two hours (one hour in the morning and one hour in the evening) along with recitation of Manas Jap: for getting and also for sustaining the harmony between, body, mind, intellect and spirit. In this way if he continues the Yogabhyas, a minimum period of six weeks will be required for maintaining and achieving harmony of the Physical aspects; a minimum of ten to twelve years for intellectual aspects and more than twelve years for spiritual aspects in an average life span of sixty to seventy years. The harmony thus achieved and sustained could be judged from his behavioural changes by

using recent scientific techniques.

Aspects of Yoga to be Introduced At Various Stages

Yama related to Social ethics deals with Ahimsa, Satya Asteya, Brahmacharya and Aparigriha. Niyama related to personal ethics deals with Saucha, Santosh, Tapa, Swadhyaya. Iswar related to pranidhana elementary or preparative stage of Asanas and Pranayamas are to be integrated in such a way that a harmony between various external behaviours of an individual is achieved. Integration of advanced stages or the psychological approaches / aspects of Asanas, Pranayams and Pratyaharas will lead to keep harmony between the internal behaviours. Dharana and Dhyana are to be integrated for intellectual behaviour while the Samadhi will help to keep harmony of the spiritual behaviour / spirituality.

Yoga practices are to be integrated in various behavioural processes:

- 1) Some practices seem to influence the external behaviour related to body.
- 2) Some practices seem to influence the internal behaviour related to mind by acting on processes which are a common integral part of the production of behaviour namely the ability to receive environmental stimuli, to consolidate, retain and restore information.
- 3) Some yogic practices seem to influence the intellectual behaviour.
- 4) Some practices seem to influence the spiritual behaviour by keeping a harmony between external.

In this manner yoga is to be integrated in modern education for recognizing the 'self' or the 'Wholeness' or the 'Iness' of the individual. Yoga should be introduced as a physical training programme up to school level, anatomically and physiologically up to high school and pre-university level, as mind - culture in colleges and as a spiritual culture at University level. During the development period of the child most of the body developments take place through physical training, games, sports or drills. Hence the yoga should be introduced as one of the parts of the physical education up to school level. As the child advances in age he becomes more mature and he knows the importance, peculiarity, merits, demerits and limitations of yogic practices and, therefore, from high school level onwards the higher and higher aspects of yoga should be introduced. In professional Institutions the advanced aspect of yoga in the form of training, treatment and research is to be introduced. An aspirant may pursue Dharana, Dhyana and Samadhi aspects of Yoga for his own self - enlightenment. Setterlind (1983) found that regular practice of meditation and yoga brings a positive change in the well-being of the subjects. Swami (1994) and Rao (1995) established that the yogic practices are good and useful as they help not only to strengthen each organ and develop every muscle of the body but also to regulate the circulation of the blood, purify the lungs, inspire the mind to be more alert, and gives a feeling of well-being and harmonious development of human personality.

Conclusion

Aside from the physical benefits of yoga, there is also the abundant proportion of mental benefits that yoga provides to you. These mental benefits areas like reducing the stress level of your body. The stress that is been previously imputed in your body would result in being revealed itself as various ways like back pain neck pain and sleeping problems. A regular practice of yoga would help you to address all these problems. Yoga is also scientifically proved to increase the concentration of a human being.

References

- [1] Birkel D. A., Edgren L. (2000). Hatha yoga: improved vital capacity of college students. *Altern. Ther. Health Med.* 6 55–63.
- [2] Colgrove Y, Sharma N, Kluding P, Potter D, Imming K, VandeHoef J, et al. Effect of Yoga on motor function in people with Parkinson's disease: A randomized, controlled pilot study. *J Yoga Phys Ther.* 2012;2:1–11.
- [3] Dhansoia V, Bhargav H, Metri K. Immediate effect of mind sound resonance technique on state anxiety and cognitive functions in patients suffering from generalized anxiety disorder: A self-controlled pilot study. *Int J Yoga.* 2015;8:70–3.
- [4] Kiecolt-Glaser J. K., Christian L., Preston H., Houts C. R., Malarkey W. B., Emery C. F., et al. (2010). Stress, inflammation, and yoga practice. *Psychosom. Med.* 72 113–121. 10.1097/PSY.0b013e3181cb9377

ADOLESCENT'S PERCEPTION LEVEL ON GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract

Different sexes play different social roles, which are indicated by gender. Gender norms are the frequently unstated guidelines that establish what qualities and actions are regarded and acceptable for males, women, and gender non-conforming people. A sample of 150 eighth standard students following Kerala State syllabus were selected for the study using random sampling technique. The sample includes boys and girls from joint and nuclear type of families. The investigator employed a descriptive survey method for the present study. A five-point scale on adolescent's perception developed by the investigator was used in carrying out the study. The main objective of the present study is to find out adolescent's perception level on gender equality and also to analyze significant differences in the perception level based on gender and family type. Various descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used for analyzing the data. The study reveals that there was a moderate level of perception among adolescents based on gender equality. The investigator also found that there exists significant difference on adolescent's perception level based on gender and based on family type.

Keywords: Adolescent, Perception, Gender Equality

Introduction

Gender equality, in any case, called sexual fairness or equalization of the genders, is the state of equivalent simple entry to resources and openings paying little heed to sex, including financial interest and fundamental administration; and the condition of esteeming different practices, desires and needs correspondingly, offering little respect to gender (Bhatia, 2020). Girls and boys see gender inequality in their homes and communities every day – in textbooks, in the media and among the adults who care for them (UNICEF, n.d.). Profound changes in identity and self-perception occur during puberty. An early adolescent is thrust into a new set of roles and expectations by the outward signs of sexual development. Puberty also causes a shift in how a young person interacts with classmates and the outside world, which influences the values and aspirations they carry into adulthood. Gender norms and the understanding of what it means to be a man or woman in a particular culture are fundamental to those ideals. Gender-equitable attitudes are often constructed during adolescence making this a critical time to alter gender perceptions. Construction of gender attitudes and perceptions of gender norms occurs during ages 10–19 years and during this time, adolescents engage with and construct their own gender-based understanding of what it means to be a boy or a girl (Blum, Mmari, & Moreau, 2017).

Need and Significance of the Study

Gender norms are considered as culturally accepted expectations regarding the traits and behaviours that men and women ought to exhibit. The largest influences on an adolescent's gender-related attitudes are also these norms. Adolescence is a time when gender norms are perceived, and during the early years of adolescence, these perceptions are still malleable. Gendered perspectives of power and social norms establish themselves in adolescence, as boys and girls begin to form senses of self, obligation, and goals during this period of rapid development (Asher, 2020). In the Indian culture, parents promote adolescent socialisation on gender roles and how to dress, act, and interact with people of the other sex, and this socialisation may be enforced physically. Through messages coming from a variety of sources in a child's surroundings, such as family, friends, school, community, the health care system, and media (such as television, advertising, video games, the internet), gender socialisation continues into adolescent development. Adolescents experience the physical, social, and emotional changes of puberty, try on several identities, and learn about love relationships throughout this period of human development. They are particularly predisposed to taking in gendered signals and engaging in gendered behaviours that help them fit in with their peer groups.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the perception level of adolescents on gender equality.
- 2) To find out whether there is a significant difference in adolescent's perception level on gender equality based on the subsample gender.

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- 3) To find out whether there is a significant difference in adolescent's perception level on gender equality based on subsample family type.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) The level of perception of adolescents on gender equality is moderate.
- 2) There is significant difference in the mean scores of adolescent's perceptions on gender equality based on the subsample gender.
- 3) There is a significant difference in the mean scores of adolescent's perceptions on gender equality based on family type.

Method Adopted for the Study

The investigator adopted normative survey method for the present study. Scale on adolescent's perception developed by the investigator was used to measure the perception level of adolescents. The scale is implemented on 150 eighth standard students following Kerala State syllabus. Descriptive statistics and t- test were the statistical techniques used for the present study.

Analysis and Interpretation

The purpose of this study is to find out the level of adolescent's perception on gender equality. The statistical analysis was carried out on the light of objectives formulated for the study. The investigator examined the hypotheses formulated for the study using the results of statistical data analysis. Analysis on Adolescent's Perception Level on Gender Equality. The analysis on adolescent's perception level on gender equality was analysed and the details are presented in table 1.

Table 1 Analysis on the adolescent's perception level on gender equality.

Level of Perception	Frequency	Percentage
High	25	16.67
Moderate	106	70.67
Low	19	12.67

By analyzing the data, the investigator got a mean value of 43.73 and standard deviation as 11.28. From table 1, it is clear that 70.67% of adolescents have moderate level of perception on gender equality, 16.67% have high level of perception on gender equality and 12.67% have low level of perception on gender equality. Test of Significance of Difference between Mean Scores of Adolescent's Perception Level on Gender Equality Based on Subsample Gender. The scores on Adolescent's perception level on gender equality for the selected subsamples were compared using the test of significance. The differences between their mean scores were computed by using the critical ratio. Details regarding the results obtained are given in the Table 2.

Table 2 Test of significance of difference between mean scores of Adolescent's perception level on gender equality based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
Boys	75	35.32	3.14	1.98	0.05
Girls	75	52.13	10.16		

From table 2, it is found that the mean score and standard deviation of adolescents belonging to Boys were 35.32 and 3.14 and that of Girls were 52.13 and 10.16 respectively with regards to adolescent's perception level on gender equality. The critical ratio obtained was 1.98, which was greater than the table value at 0.05 level. This showed that there was significant difference in the adolescent's perception level on gender equality with regards to gender. Test of Significance of Difference between Mean Scores of Adolescent's Perception Level on Gender Equality based on Subsample Family Type. The scores on Adolescent's perception level on gender equality for the selected subsamples were compared using the test of significance. The differences between their mean scores were computed by using the critical ratio.

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Table 3 Test of significance of difference between mean scores of Adolescent's perception level on gender equality based on Family type.

Family Type	Frequency	Mean	SD	CR	Level of Significance
Joint	81	35.81	3.42	1.99	0.05
Nuclear	72	52.68	10.01		

From table 3, it is found that the mean score and standard deviation of adolescents belonging to Joint family were 35.81 and 3.42 and that of Nuclear were 52.68 and 10.01 respectively with regards to adolescent's perception level on gender equality. The critical ratio obtained was 1.99, which was greater than the table value at 0.05 level. This showed that there was significant difference in the adolescent's perception level on gender equality with regards to family type.

Findings of the Study

The study intends to find out the perception level of adolescents on gender equality. The present study was conducted among 150 adolescent students (STD. 8) under Kerala state syllabus including Joint and Nuclear family type. From the study, the investigator found that, majority of the adolescents possess moderate level of perception on gender equality. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in the perception level of adolescents on gender equality with respect to gender and family type. The investigator can identify that the perception level of Girls on gender equality is higher than that of Boys. The investigator also analysed that the students belonging to nuclear family type possess high level of perception on gender equality when compared to that of students belonging to joint family type.

Educational Implications

- 1) Gender-sensitization programmes can influence how adolescents form and change their attitudes on gender, potentially affecting both their short- and long-term beliefs.
- 2) Placing adolescents at the centre of strategies that increase gender equality and it can be start with early adolescence.
- 3) Programs that promote gender empowerment and gender sensitization among young people have the potential to reduce gender inequality in the long run since they are targeted at a time when these individuals are still formulating their gender attitudes.

Conclusion

Adopted gender norms throughout adolescence reflect and reinforce unequal hierarchies, which have an adverse effect on the health of those young people later in life as well as the health of the children in the upcoming generation. Teenagers have the chance to modify their short- and long-term gender views by bringing up gender equality since individual perceptions of gender norms begin to take shape in early adolescence and are still malleable. Adolescents are under increasing pressure to conform to the socially acceptable gender roles and are becoming more aware of the standards they must meet as either men or women. As they accept, reject, or alter gender norms, young adolescents actively participate in this process, which is subject to changes.

References

- [1] Aishwarya Bhatia, (2020). Gender equality. Gender Equality - Indian Law Portal
- [2] Blum, R. W., Mmari, K., & Moreau, C. (2017). It begins at 10 how gender expectations shape early adolescence around the world. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 61(4).
- [3] Jha, S. S., Dasgupta, A., Paul, B., Ghosh, P., & Biswas, A. (2020). Attitude and perception of gender equity among students and teachers of a rural school in West Bengal: A mixed-method approach. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 9, 330. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_597_20
- [4] UNICEF (n.d.) Gender equality. Gender equality | UNICEF World Health Organization. WHO Women and Gender Equity. World Health Organization; http://www.who.int/social_determinants/themes/womenandgender/en/

INFLUENCE OF PARENTS EDUCATION ON THE PERFORMACE OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN INTERNATIUNAL SUBJECT AFTER COVID IN DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract

One of the most vital instruments for communication in the world is the English language. Due to its widespread use and significance throughout the world, learning English is a subject that is required in all situations when English is being used as a second or foreign language. The present paper focuses on the influence of parents education on the performace of high school students in International subject after covid in digital era. The study has been carried out with a sample of 630 school students of Anantapur district , Andhra Pradesh. The students achieved marks in formative and summative assessments conducted Board Secondary School, Andhra Pradesh. The data is collected by evaluation or assessment method in a stratified random sampling. The main object of the study is to find achievement levels of among illiterates, X class, Graduate and Postgraduate and above, high school students parents education of Kurnool district in English subject . The mean, SD, t test and F-ratio statistics is used for thestudy at 0.05 and 0.01 significant level. It is found that t there is a significant difference between VIII AND IX class students in FA1, FA2 and FA3, but there is no significant difference among X class students in FA1, FA2 and FA3 in the achievement levels in English subject with respect to student parent in education. There is a significant difference between VIII AND IX class students in SA1, SA2 and over all assessment FA3 in the achievement levels in English subject with respect to student parent in education.

Keywords: *English, Significant, Parents, Achivement*

Introduction

One of the most vital instruments for communication in the world is the English language. Due to its widespread use and significance throughout the world, learning English is a subject that is required in all situations when English is being used as a second or foreign language. As a primary predictor of reading, word identification and acquisition are also important skills (Nathan & Stanovich, 1991). Therefore, kids' achievement as lifelong readers depends greatly on their ability in sight word recognition (Weakland, 2013). In today's world of worldwide business and technology-based sectors, the English language is extensively employed and is one of the most efficient forms of communication. The significance of English has been acknowledged by India, which has implemented a number of educational measures to raise the level of English language proficiency among its population. India, a multilingual nation, depicts a linguistically diverse culture, but one in which English is emphasised by decision-makers as the route to modernisation. Apart from their mother tongue and other native tongues, pupils must acquire English since it is a language with significant global influence. Following independence, the Indian government established a number of commissions and committees to examine the issues with the nation's educational system as a whole and provide solutions for improvement. At different levels of schooling, the commissions also take into account the English language problem and give it the attention it deserves. The University Education Commission said in 1948 that "English, nevertheless, must be continued to be studied" after realising the value of the English language. A humanistic and technical language, it has a wealth of literature. We would disconnect from the live stream of ever expanding information if, motivated by sentimental emotions, we gave up English. The Secondary Education Commission of 1952 endorsed the study of English and stated, "It should be recognised that even with regard to many of the diverse courses in instruction as matters stand at this time, a knowledge of English will be extremely useful for understanding the subject matter and for further study of the subject." As English will be required as a library language in the field of higher education for a very long time to come, a solid foundation in the language will have to be laid at the school stage, according to the

Kothari Commission of 1964, which also placed emphasis on learning English as a foreign language. In light of this, the panel suggested using the three-language formula: First, one's mother tongue or a local tongue. (2) Hindi, the union's official language; alternatively, if Hindi isn't used, English, the associate official language. (3) An international or contemporary language. Currently, English is used as the primary teaching language and the language of most textbooks. In the present study investigation made on influence of parents education on the performance of high school students in international subject after covid in digital era.

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Anantapur district. The data is collected by using evaluation or assessment method. The total data collected 6 high schools of Anantapur district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy. Tools: Formative and summative Question papers preppers Board of secondary school, Andhra Pradesh. 3 Formative each for 20 marks and 2 summative assessment are conducted for 80 marks. Personal data sheet.

Fig 1 : Sample size of high school students in respect to their parents qualification

Objectives of the Study

To study the influence of parents education on the performance of high school students in international subject after covid in digital era.

Hypothesis of the Study

There would be no significant difference among parents of high school students with respect to their education on the achievement levels in English subject.

Statistical Techniques Used

The data thus collected and scored was analyzed by using relevant statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation and t – test. The usual levels of significance, viz., 0.05, and 0.01 were used to test the significance of the obtained statistics

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Results and Discussion

Table 1: ANOVA of Achievement levels of VIII Class high school students according to their Parents Education.

PE		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
FA1	Between Groups	1193.672	3	397.891	34.737**
	Within Groups	2359.609	206	11.454	
	Total	3553.281	209		
FA2	Between Groups	811.714	3	270.571	27.630**
	Within Groups	2017.282	206	9.793	
	Total	2828.995	209		
FA3	Between Groups	772.102	3	257.367	26.896**
	Within Groups	1971.179	206	9.569	
	Total	2743.281	209		
SA1	Between Groups	10051.342	3	3350.447	33.897**
	Within Groups	20361.686	206	98.843	
	Total	30413.029	209		
SA2	Between Groups	7907.712	3	2635.904	42.938**
	Within Groups	12645.983	206	61.388	
	Total	20553.695	209		
TOTAL	Between Groups	75544.616	3	25181.539	43.307**
	Within Groups	119780.912	206	581.461	
	Total	195325.529	209		

Table 2: ANOVA of Achievement levels of IX Class high school students according to their Parents Education

PE		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
FA1	Between Groups	644.411	3	214.804	15.183**
	Within Groups	2914.355	206	14.147	
	Total	3558.767	209		
FA2	Between Groups	615.834	3	205.278	17.166**
	Within Groups	2463.423	206	11.958	
	Total	3079.257	209		
FA3	Between Groups	443.496	3	147.832	17.037
	Within Groups	1787.499	206	8.677	
	Total	2230.995	209		
SA1	Between Groups	7483.952	3	2494.651	30.261
	Within Groups	16982.315	206	82.438	
	Total	24466.267	209		
SA2	Between Groups	6011.704	3	2003.901	28.293
	Within Groups	14590.220	206	70.826	
	Total	20601.924	209		
TOTAL	Between Groups	53444.036	3	17814.679	28.545
	Within Groups	128561.031	206	624.083	
	Total	182005.067	209		

Table 3: ANOVA of Achievement levels of X Class high school students according to their Parents Education

PE		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
FA1	Between Groups	67.416	3	22.472	1.656@
	Within Groups	2781.369	205	13.568	
	Total	2848.785	208		

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FA2	Between Groups	81.877	3	27.292	2.039@
	Within Groups	2744.372	205	13.387	
	Total	2826.249	208		
FA3	Between Groups	81.922	3	27.307	2.931*
	Within Groups	1909.868	205	9.316	
	Total	1991.789	208		
SA1	Between Groups	3640.983	3	1213.661	5.484**
	Within Groups	45367.447	205	221.305	
	Total	49008.431	208		
SA2	Between Groups	4055.427	3	1351.809	6.894**
	Within Groups	40196.496	205	196.080	
	Total	44251.923	208		
TOTAL	Between Groups	20442.247	3	6814.082	4.999**
	Within Groups	279429.447	205	1363.070	
	Total	299871.694	208		

Table 4: Means, SD' values of achievement levels of high school students according to their Parents Education

Assessment	Class	Parents Education	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value
FA 1	VIII	Illiterate	93	12.8065	3.55166	t ₁₂ =2.626**
		X class	60	11.3167	3.34204	t ₂₃ =9.392**
		Graduate	50	17.3273	3.16260	t ₃₄ =2.266*
		Post Graduate and above	7	19.0000	1.5000	t ₁₃ =7.545** t ₂₄ =10.784** t ₄₁ =9.161**
	IX	Illiterate	105	13.2222	3.87740	t ₁₂ =0.434@
		X class	57	12.9298	4.20399	t ₂₃ =6.628**
		Graduate	41	17.3415	2.75327	t ₃₄ =0.459@
		Post Graduate and above	7	17.7500	2.06155	t ₁₃ =7.838** t ₂₄ =5.033** t ₄₁ =5.227**
	X	Illiterate	116	12.9358	3.62674	t ₁₂ =0.888@
		X class	70	13.4342	3.75352	t ₂₃ =1.667@
		Graduate	19	14.9474	3.43954	t ₃₄ =0.680@
		Post Graduate and above	5	13.4000	4.77493	t ₁₃ =1.764@ t ₂₄ =0.016@ t ₄₁ =0.215@
FA 2	VIII	Illiterate	93	13.3441	3.42146	t ₁₂ =2.408**
		X class	60	12.0833	2.98182	t ₂₃ =9.077**
		Graduate	50	17.0727	2.77458	t ₃₄ =1.790@
		Post Graduate and above	7	18.0000	0.89500	t ₁₃ =7.048** t ₂₄ =11.546** t ₄₁ =9.498**
	IX	Illiterate	105	13.6111	3.82523	t ₁₂ =0.863@
		X class	57	13.0877	3.60694	t ₂₃ =7.985**
		Graduate	41	17.4634	2.02605	t ₃₄ =-1.782@
		Post Graduate and above	7	18.5000	1.29099	t ₁₃ =8.379** t ₂₄ =7.926** t ₄₁ =7.958**
	X	Illiterate	116	13.3578	3.65281	t ₁₂ =1.447@
		X class	70	14.1579	3.65533	t ₂₃ =1.285@
		Graduate	19	15.3684	3.63945	t ₃₄ =0.290@

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		Post Graduate and above	5	14.8000	3.96232	t ₁₃ =2.231* t ₂₄ =0.352@ t ₄₁ =0.799@
FA 3	VIII	Illiterate	93	13.8172	3.56903	t ₁₂ =1.705@
		X class	60	12.9500	2.70232	t ₂₃ =9.259**
		Graduate	50	17.6545	2.61207	t ₃₄ =2.300*
		Post Graduate and above	7	19.0000	1.20000	t ₁₃ =7.338** t ₂₄ =10.573** t ₄₁ =8.854**
	IX	Illiterate	105	14.3796	3.28610	t ₁₂ =0.013@
		X class	57	14.3860	2.95051	t ₂₃ =7.412**
		Graduate	41	17.8293	1.89608	t ₃₄ =2.621**
		Post Graduate and above	7	18.7500	0.50000	t ₁₃ =8.469** t ₂₄ =10.053** t ₄₁ =11.741**
	X	Illiterate	116	14.2844	3.01874	t ₁₂ =2.169*
		X class	70	15.2632	2.95914	t ₂₃ =0.913@
		Graduate	19	16.0526	3.43954	t ₃₄ =0.028@
		Post Graduate and above	5	16.0000	3.74166	t ₁₃ =2.112* t ₂₄ =0.431@ t ₄₁ =1.011@
SA 1	VIII	Illiterate	93	57.0000	10.38184	t ₁₂ =-0.805@
		X class	60	58.4500	11.18174	t ₂₃ =8.077**
		Graduate	50	72.9455	7.53859	t ₃₄ =-2.743**
		Post Graduate and above	7	76.0000	0.85000	t ₁₃ =-10.524** t ₂₄ =11.867@ t ₄₁ =16.912**
	IX	Illiterate	105	59.1852	10.22563	t ₁₂ =2.286**
		X class	57	62.8772	9.58434	t ₂₃ =8.648**
		Graduate	41	74.6829	3.79104	t ₃₄ =1.102@
		Post Graduate and above	7	72.5000	5.00000	t ₁₃ =13.873** t ₂₄ =4.227** t ₄₁ =6.230**
	X	Illiterate	116	65.3119	13.39271	t ₁₂ =2.524*
		X class	70	70.9211	15.41407	t ₂₃ =1.195@
		Graduate	19	76.8421	20.05344	t ₃₄ =0.551@
		Post Graduate and above	5	81.0000	15.31339	t ₁₃ =2.419* t ₂₄ =1.608@ t ₄₁ =2.565*
SA 2	VIII	Illiterate	93	59.2043	8.33348	t ₁₂ =2.247*
		X class	60	62.3833	8.67510	t ₂₃ =-8.238**
		Graduate	50	73.8182	5.79940	t ₃₄ =2.570*
		Post Graduate and above	7	76.5000	1.70711	t ₁₃ =12.266** t ₂₄ =-10.922** t ₄₁ =16.038**
	IX	Illiterate	105	61.6667	9.71077	t ₁₂ =2.898**
		X class	57	66.0000	8.73212	t ₂₃ =8.078**
		Graduate	41	75.6585	2.28703	t ₃₄ =2.974**
		Post Graduate and above	7	72.5000	2.64575	t ₁₃ =14.063** t ₂₄ =4.251** t ₄₁ =7.863**
	X	Illiterate	116	68.0275	13.68323	t ₁₂ =3.463**
		X class	70	75.2105	13.71551	t ₂₃ =1.158@

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		Graduate	19	80.0526	16.77456	$t_{34}=0.007@$
		Post Graduate and above	5	80.0000	14.15980	$t_{13}=-2.967^{**}$
Total	VIII	Illiterate	93	156.1720	24.69757	$t_{24}=-0.732@$
		X class	60	157.1833	26.20745	$t_{41}=1.854@$
		Graduate	50	198.8182	20.70077	$t_{12}=0.238@$
		Post Graduate and above	7	208.5000	1.80711	$t_{23}=9.306^{**}$
	IX	Illiterate	105	162.0648	28.05411	$t_{34}=3.221^{**}$
		X class	57	169.2807	26.58796	$t_{13}=-10.964^{**}$
		Graduate	41	202.9756	10.55814	$t_{24}=14.867^{**}$
		Post Graduate and above	7	200.0000	10.03328	$t_{41}=19.742^{**}$
	X	Illiterate	116	172.6514	33.55189	$t_{12}=1.618@$
		X class	70	186.4737	38.40121	$t_{23}=8.892^{**}$
		Graduate	19	201.0526	47.52365	$t_{34}=0.720@$
		Post Graduate and above	5	205.2000	40.61650	$t_{13}=13.307^{**}$
						$t_{41}=8.111^{**}$
						$t_{12}=2.492^*$
						$t_{23}=-1.232@$
						$t_{34}=0.196@$
						$t_{13}=2.505^*$
						$t_{24}=1.000@$
						$t_{41}=1.766@$

The influence of parents education on the achievement levels in English subject is calculated and tabulated in table 4.10, 4.10.1, 4.10.2 and 4.10.3. The total sample of students parents is 630 out of which VIII class students parents who are illiterate is 95, X class 60, graduates 50 and post graduate and above are 7. IX class students parents who are illiterate is 105, X class 57, graduates 41 and post graduate and above are 7. X class students parents who are illiterate is 116, X class 70, graduates 19 and post graduate and above are 5. In Formative assessment 1, The F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 34.737, 15.113. which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above. The F ratio value of X class student parents education values is 1.650, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in FA1. VIII class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 2.626, 9.392, 2.266, 7.545, 10.784 and 9.161, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA1. IX class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 26.628, 7.838, 5.033 and 5.227, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. post graduate and above and illiterate in FA1.

In Formative assessment 2, The F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 27.631, 26.896, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above. The F ratio value of X class student parents education values is 2.039, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in FA2. VIII class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 2.408, 9.077, 7.048, 11.546 and 9.498, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA2. t values of graduate and post graduate and above is 21.790, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence

the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between VIII students parents of graduate and post graduate and above, in FA2. IX class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 7.985, 8.379, 7.926 and 7.958, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between IX students parents of X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA2. The t values of illiterate and X class, graduate and post graduate and above, are 0.863 and 1.782, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between IX students parents of of illiterate and X class, graduate and post graduate and above, in FA2. X class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 1.447, 1.285, 0.290, 0.352 and 0.799, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between X students parents of of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA2. The t values of illiterate and graduate is 2.231 which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is a significant difference between X students parents illiterate and graduate in FA2

In Formative assessment 3, The F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 26.896, 17.037, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above. The F ratio value of X class student parents education values is 2.931, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in FA3. VIII class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 9.259, 2.300, 7.338, 10.573 and 8.854, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA3. The t values of illiterate and X class is 1.705, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between VIII students parents of graduate and post graduate and ab illiterate and X class in FA3. IX class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 7.412, 2.621, 8.469, 10.053 and 11.741, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between IX students parents of of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA3. The t values of illiterate and X class is 0.013, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between IX students parents of graduate and post graduate and ab illiterate and X class in FA3. X class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class illiterate and graduate are 2.169 and 2.112, which is significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between X students parents of of illiterate and X class illiterate and graduate in FA3. The t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 0.913, 0.028, 0.431 and 1.011, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in FA3.

In summative assessment 1 The F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 33.897, 30.261 and 5.484 which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in SA1. VIII class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 8.077, 2.743, 10.524 and 16.912, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA1. The t values of illiterate and X class, X class and post graduate and a above is 0.805 and

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11.867 which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between VIII students parents of illiterate and X class, X class and post graduate and a above SA1. IX class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 2.286, 8.648, 13.873, 4.227 and 6.23, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between IX students parents of illiterate and X class X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA1. The t values of graduate and post graduate and above is 1.102, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between IX students parents graduate and post graduate and above in SA1. X class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, illiterate and graduate are 3.463 and 2.967, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between X students parents of illiterate and X class X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA1. The t values of of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate is 1.158, 0.007, 0.732 and 1.854, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between X students parents X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA1. In summative assessment 2 The F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 42.938, 28.293 and 6.894 which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in SA2. VIII class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 2.247, 8.238, 2.570, 12.266, 10.922 and 16.038, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA2. IX class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 2.898, 8.078, 2.974, 14.063, 4.251 and 7.863, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. X class students parents education t values of illiterate and X class, illiterate and graduate are 3.463 and 2.967, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between X students parents of illiterate and X class X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA2. The t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate is 1.158, 0.007, 0.732 and 1.854, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between X students parents X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, X class and post graduate and a above X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in SA2.

In overall assessment the F ratio values of VIII, IX class student parents education values are 43.309, 28.545 and 4.999 which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class students parents who are illiterate, X class, graduate and post graduate and above in overall assessment. VIII class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate are 9.306, 3.221, 10.964, 14.867 and 9.742, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. There fore there is a significant difference between VIII students parents of X class and graduate, graduate and post graduate and above, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a above, post graduate and above and illiterate in over all assessment. The t values of illiterate and X class is 0.238, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between VIII students parents of of illiterate and X class, in overall assessment. IX class students parents education t values of X class and graduate, illiterate and graduate, X class and post graduate and a above, X class and post graduate and a

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above , post graduate and above and illiterate are 8.892, 13.307, 5.936 and 8.111, which is significant at 0.01 level , hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Fig 2. Means, SD' values of achievement levels of high school students according to their Parents Education.

Conclusion

There is a significant difference between VIII AND IX class students in FA1, FA2 and FA3, but there is no significant difference among X class students in FA1, FA2 and FA3 in the achievement levels in English subject with respect to student parent in education. There is a significant difference between VIII AND IX class students in SA1, SA2 and over all assessment FA3 in the achievement levels in English subject with respect to student parent in education.

References

- [1] AlHaddad, S. K., Mohamed, M., & Al Habshi, S. M. (2004). An exploratory study on English language proficiency and academic performance in the context of globalization of accounting education. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting* 2(1), 55-71.
- [2] Ghenghesh, P. (2015): The Relationship between English Language Proficiency and Academic Performance of University Students – Should Academic Institutions Really be concerned, *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*. 4(2), 91-97.
- [3] Maleki, A., & Zangani, E. (2007). A survey on the relationship between English language proficiency and the academic achievement of Iranian EFL students, *Asian EFL Journal*, 9(1), 86-96.

SCIENCE OF YOGA AND BASIC QUALITIES BEHIND THE GOOD YOGA TEACHER

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Abstract

Yoga is the science of the SELF. Yoga can also be termed the science of man in depth, the science of conscious evolution or the science of human possibilities. Yoga not only has the concepts but also the tools and technology needed to find OUR SELF. While the modern science looks outward the Yogi searches the depth of his own self. According to Yogamaharishi Dr Swami Gitananda Giri Guru Maharaj who was one of the foremost authorities on Rishiculture Ashtanga Yoga in the last century, Yoga is a science and not only is it a science but is the mother of Science.

Keywords: *Yoga, Science, Teaching, Teacher*

Introduction

According to 'Science Manpower Project', "Science is a cumulative and endless series of empirical observation which result in the formation of concepts & theories, with both concepts & theories being subject of modification in the light of further empirical observation. Science is both a body of knowledge & the process of acquiring & refining knowledge." Science is organized and systematized learning. Science is a body of cumulative and ordered observations. Science is a process as well as the product. The characteristic of a science or Vidya is the approach and not merely content or quality of knowledge. Though Yoga has its foundations more than 5000 years ago and is principally an oral tradition, the verbal basis of Yoga-Vidya (Yogic Science) is found in the Upanishads (especially the Katha-Upanishad, Shvetashvatara Upanishad and Maitrayaniya-Upanishad), the Yoga Sutras of Patanjali and the Bhagavad Gita.

Essential Qualities of a Good Yoga Teacher

- 1) Must be a good learner and ready to also learn through the process of teaching
- 2) Must have a strong self-introspective ability
- 3) Must be disciplined and dedicated towards the cause of Yoga
- 4) Must have a sound knowledge of the Yoga principles and techniques along with an understanding of the precautions, contraindications etc that are involved
- 5) Must have an understanding of the holistic nature of Yoga physiology, philosophy and psychology
- 6) Must possess a strong desire for spiritual evolution
- 7) Must be willing to learn from all situations and not have an, "I know it all!" attitude.
- 8) Must possess a sense of empathy for others
- 9) Must be willing to sublimate their own EGO
- 10) Must have a good sense of humor and be able to laugh at them without reservation.
- 11) Must be able to motivate others by self-example and lead the way as a true Yoga Acharya.
- 12) Must learn from their mistakes and be ready to correct them when they have made such mistakes
- 13) Must have devotion to the Guru who has guided them to the level of becoming a teacher themselves. Guru Droha or treachery to one's Guru is considered the worst sin.

General Instructions for Yoga Teachers

- 1) Choose a natural setting with some trees, plants in an open area or a roof top. If in a hall, please open the windows to improve the ventilation.
- 2) Make sure that all the mats are in a line and well organized. Discipline at all levels is an important aspect of Yoga.
- 3) Make sure there is an adequate supply of water during the class. Proper hydration is to be maintained at all times.
- 4) Try to keep the teacher student relationship in a traditional form as a Guru Kula atmosphere. Without such a relationship real teaching cannot occur.
- 5) Give proper advice on the comfortable Yoga dress to be worn for the class. Cultural aspects must be

- understood with regards to the dressing.
- 6) Make sure that you have already clearly explained the necessity of having an empty stomach before performing any of the Yoga practices.
 - 7) Try to have the classes in the morning and emphasize the importance of facing the morning sun while doing the practices.
 - 8) Help the students to become aware of what they are doing and what is happening with every movement in the class. Becoming aware of how unaware we are is the first step to be emphasized.
 - 9) Clarify the right and left confusion that tends to occur during the practices.
 - 10) Suggestions for a healthy diet and life style should be given as appropriate. The importance of stopping the negative habits must be emphasized as much as possible.
 - 11) Try to give a detailed view of the practices that are being taught. For e.g. when teaching the Surya Namaskar, make sure that you explain the concepts of the Usha Shakthi, names of the sun with their meaning, importance of breath-movement coordination etc. The cultural understanding should also be developed at all times.
 - 12) Yoga is a way of life and not just a few techniques. It is important to discuss the principles such as the Yama-Niyama when appropriate.
 - 13) Give them an understanding of the various paths of Yoga, the different traditions, the types of Sadhakas and the importance of Guru Bhakti and Guru Dakshina (gratitude to the Guru) in the evolutionary process. Shraddha or faith in the Guru and their wisdom is essential for all students.

For the Yoga Teacher

Nowadays, teachers are devoid of noble thoughts and attitudes. They work for their salary and lack commitment, noble qualities and dedication to their work. Come exams and they go on strike! How can such teachers inspire the students? As a yoga teacher, you should be an acharya, a guru and strive to become a rishi. Then you can impart knowledge of material sciences (apara vidya) as well as the spiritual knowledge (para vidya / brahm vidya). Spiritual background will help students to do better in material sciences as well and they will progress in their profession. In Vedic India, gurukul system of education gave equal importance to material as well as spiritual knowledge. Treat all students equal, irrespective of social or economic status. Remember that the great Yogeshwar Krishn and his buddy, humble Sudama (Kuselan) studied together in the same gurukul.

Conclusion

Swami Vivekananda said, "Yoga is really one of the grandest sciences...take up the study of this science as you would any other science of material nature and remember there is no mystery and no danger in it."The process of Yoga is one of the understanding and achievement of Mind Control. We can't live happy life without Science. There is no definition of general science or science which is universally accepted. In general we can define science as an accumulated and systematized learning in general usage restricted to natural phenomenon. Science is the activity where truthfulness is obviously an essential condition for success. Its success is measured by its truthfulness. Yoga Teacher must have a strong self-introspective ability and must be disciplined and dedicated towards the cause of Yoga.

References

- [1] Gitananda Giri Swami. Frankly Speaking. Satya Press, Pondicherry, 1997.
- [2] Feuerstein Georg. The Shambala Guide to Yoga. Shambala Publications Inc, Boston, Massachusetts, and USA.1996.
- [3] Gitananda Giri Swami. Yoga the Art and Science of Awareness. Souvenir 1996; 4th International Yoga Festival, Govt of Pondicherry.
- [4] Yoga: Science of Holistic Living. Vivekananda Kendra Patrika. 17-2 1988.
- [5] Chidbhavananda Swami. The Bhagavad Gita. Ramakrishna Tapovanam, Trichy, 1984

TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR DIVERSIFIED CLASSROOM

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Abstract

Students with different types races, culture, family, genders, socioeconomic backgrounds and intellectual abilities in class room that considered as a diversified classroom. The teacher has no partiality among the diversified classroom. The teacher keeps their ethnicity and devotion in their teaching and learning process at diversified classroom situations. When teacher has high expectation that time teacher create a high academic achievement among students and also create high academic achievers. If otherwise teacher has low expectation that teacher creates a low achievers. Communicate a belief in the academic potential of all pupils' by using language that promotes challenge. Demonstrate consistently high behavioural expectations' by creating a culture of trust and respect in the classroom.Following strategies are adopted by teacher in diversified classroom. 1. Diversified classroom demonstration of high expectations. 2. Implementation of culturally relevant instructionCooperative learning, Capitalize on the funds of knowledge in families and the community's diverse classrooms, cognitive guided instruction, Technology enriched instruction, 3.Establishment of Caring Relationships and 4. Parent and community are Involvement in students' progressive development.

Introduction

Students in our nation's classrooms today are more diverse than ever. They represent different races, ethnicities, cultures, and socioeconomic backgrounds, and they speak many different languages. Further, these students often exhibit a wide range of academic, physical and social abilities or skills.

Meaning of Diversified Classroom

Students with different types races, culture, family, genders, socioeconomic backgrounds and intellectual abilities in class room.

Teaching Strategies for Diversified Classroom

- 1) Diversified classroom demonstration of high expectations
- 2) Implementation of culturally relevant instruction
 - a. Cooperative learning
 - b. Capitalize on the funds of knowledge in families and the community's diverse classrooms
 - c. Cognitive guided instruction
 - d. Technology enriched instruction
- 3) Establishment of Caring Relationships
- 4) parent and community Involvement

1. Diversified Classroom Demonstration of High Expectations

When teacher has high expectation that time teacher create a high academic achievement among students and also create high academic achievers. If otherwise teacher has low expectation that teacher creates a low achievers. Communicate a belief in the academic potential of all pupils' by using language that promotes challenge. Demonstrate consistently high behavioural expectations' by creating a culture of trust and respect in the classroom.

2. Implementation of Culturally Relevant Instruction

a. Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning, also called small-group learning, is one teaching method that can help students learn academic material and social skills. Understanding more about cooperative learning can help you create a positive social experience in your classroom. In this article, we examine some common cooperative learning strategies, discuss the benefits of using these strategies and provide tips to help you use cooperative learning in diversified classroom. During small-group interactions, they find many opportunities to reflect upon and reply to

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the diverse responses fellow learners bring to the questions raised. Small groups also allow students to add their perspectives to an issue based on their cultural differences.

b. Capitalize on the funds of knowledge in families and the communities' diverse classrooms

Also included in this judgement is the term cultural capital, which is defined as: “the essential knowledge that children need to be educated citizens”. It goes on to say: Cultural capital is the essential knowledge that children need to prepare them for their future success. Young children's interests develop in the context of their relationships with the people, places and experiences they encounter in their daily lives.

c. Cognitive Guided Instruction

The human mind has an innate, or built-in, ability to understand logic and scientific, and different people have different ways of developing that knowledge. Sometimes it is extremely valuable to allow your students to choose their own path toward learning. Cognitively guided instruction is an approach to teaching that is based on the developmental stage of the student and the process of asking questions to help guide the students toward finding their own approaches for learning at diversified classroom.

3. Establishment of Caring Relationships

- 1) Establish relationships early on. Allow your students a glimpse at who you are outside of the classroom. ...
- 2) Build relevance between your classroom and your students' lives. ...
- 3) Create space for curiosity and discovery...
- 4) Inspire confidence in each student in your classroom.

4. Parent and Community Involvement

When parents, families and members of the community are involved with schools, all children benefit. Adult participation sends the message that school is important and the work children do there is worthy of adult attention.

- 1) Improves academic engagement
- 2) Increases life success in the long term
- 3) Helps students choose higher-level programs
- 4) A decrease in the school dropout.

Consider the Following Statistics

During the 2010–2011 school year, 54% of public school students were White and 46% were students of color. It is estimated that students in the United States represent more than 1,000 cultures. In 2011, 21% of school-age students lived in poor households. About 4.7 million students in the United States have limited English proficiency, and 11.2 million speak a language other than English at home. In many school districts, students and families speak over 100 different languages. During the 2011–2012 school year, approximately 11% of public school students ages 6–17 received special education services.

Conclusion

Students in a classroom come from a variety of backgrounds with different experiences inclusive classrooms will encourage students to tap in to their talents and abilities while developing their unique personalities and creative nature. Students obtaining a in depth cognitive structure when they work with a students from a variety of backgrounds and cultures present in the classroom.

References

- [1] Megan Lahey 2009. Technology-enriched learning environments : creating a classroom environment for the 21st century University of Northern Iowa.
- [2] Henry L. Johnson 2004, State Superintendent of Education 359 North West Street Jackson, MS 39201 (601) 359-3513

EFFECT OF COMPUTER WITH SCREEN READER ON WRITING SKILL OF STUDENT WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Education is a means of educating people about their rights and responsibilities to their families, society, and nation by providing knowledge, skills, techniques, and information. It broadens the scope and vision of the world. Reading and writing require specific abilities such as attention, vocabulary, fluency, sentence construction, cohesion, and memory, which come from immediate experience with oral and written language. Listening to stories about the world around them can help children learn to read and write. Reading and writing are the core elements of education. The vast majority of information is conveyed in writing. Students with visual impairment must interact with large print or Braille on a regular and active basis in order to read and write. The purpose of this paper is to assess the impact of a computer equipped with a screen reader on the writing of student with visual impairment. The case study method was adopted. The study focused on a single case of a blind 10-year-old female student with visual impairment. A teacher-made rating scale was used in education to assess the writing ability of student with visual impairment. The qualitative method was used to evaluate the performance of the chosen sample. The study's findings indicate that using a computer with a screen reader has a significant impact on writing skill of student with visual impairment.

Introduction

Writing is an art form. It is an essential part of communication. Good writing skills make the message simple and easy to understand. Rather than performance, the student demonstrates his or her knowledge in this manner. Each student has a different level of writing and reading ability. Handwriting and composition skills are both required for writing. Writing requires vision, which is extremely difficult for students with visual impairment. Visual impairment refers to a significant loss of vision, even if the person wears corrective lenses. Because the nature, level, and severity of visual impairment can vary greatly, each student may require individual adaptations to instructional practises and materials in order to learn effectively. Student with visual impairment requires an alternative method of writing that makes use of technology. Braille is a reading and writing medium for students with visual impairment, but it is time consuming.

Importance of Technology

More technologies are now available for students with visual impairment in today's world. Assistive technology and devices can help students with visual impairment become as independent as non-disabled students in all aspects of life. An assistive technology device is any item, piece of equipment, or product system, whether purchased commercially, modified, or customised, that is used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of people with disabilities [The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) of 2004]. Any service that directly assists a person with a disability in the selection, purchase, or application of an assistive technology device is considered an assistive technology service. The term encompasses assessing needs, selecting, designing, fitting, customising, adapting, applying, retaining, repairing, and providing technical assistance to disabled children, family members, or professionals (Sah, 2010).

Screen Reader

Screen reader software is an essential part of assistive technology for the visually impaired. A screen reader is software that runs on various devices and is used to access digital content by many blind and low-vision people. The screen reader reads out the content on the screen and provides feedback as the user interacts with the device. A screen reader user typically navigates by using the keyboard or unique gestures, but different users have varying levels of skill in manipulating inaccessible content with various tools and shortcuts. When users type the text, it will be converted into speech. If appropriate keyboard practice was provided, student with visual impairment could write the words. Reading practise is necessary after typing practise in order to correct errors.

Non-Visual Desktop Access (NVDA)

NVDA is a free screen reader that enables people with visual impairment to use computers on their own. It reads the text on the screen clearly in a computerised voice. Individuals can control what is read to them by dragging their mouse cursor to the relevant area of text or using their keyboard's arrow keys. If the computer user has a Braille display, they can also convert the text to braille format. Many blind people rely on screen readers to get an education and find work.

Writing

Writing is a very interesting and engrossing activity that can help users feel focused and concentrated. It re-creates or brings to light an individual's inner potential. The writing process is more valuable and rewarding. It provides the thrill of discovery. Writing, according to Hunt (2000) & Sampson (2004), aids in self-development and self-awareness. Writing is necessary for students to communicate and learn how the parts of language interact with one another (Banat, 2007).

Low Vision

As per the Rights of Persons with Disabilities act, (RPwD) 2016, “low-vision” means a condition where a person has any of the following conditions, namely: Visual acuity not exceeding 6/18 or lower than 20/60 up to 3/60 or up to 10/200 (Snellen) in the better eye with possible corrections; or Limitation of the field of vision subtending an angle of lower than 40 degrees up to 10 degrees.

Blindness

As per the Rights of Persons with Disabilities act, 2016, “blindness” means a condition where a person has any of the following conditions, after best correction: Total absence of sight; or Visual acuity less than 3/60 or lower than 10/200 (Snellen) in the better eye with best possible correction; or Limitation of the field of vision subtending an angle of lower than 10 degrees.

Need of the Study

The Information and Communication Technology section's goal is to present literature on the use of technology to support academic learning and engagement of students with disabilities. Developing technological skills in students with visual impairment boosts self-confidence and self-esteem, promotes inclusive education, allows them to pursue a life independently in education, jobs, and the environment, and aids them in accessing information from their surroundings. Typing is a necessary skill for students with visual impairment to improve their writing skills. In today's world, technology is crucial in the education of students with visual impairment. Students with visual impairment can use a screen reader to write, read, listen, and access whatever information they require from the internet, communicate with others, learn different languages, write and read different languages, travel independently, acquire knowledge, and write exams without the assistance of a scribe.

Statement of the Problem

Students with visual impairments rely on teachers, peer groups, and parents to learn subjects in school. Students with visual impairment can benefit greatly from the use of a Braille slate and stylus, a Braille, and recording devices when writing and reading. This procedure is also time consuming. Computers with screen readers are critical tools for students with visual impairments who want to improve their writing skills. It enables visually impaired students to access information independently in an inclusive setting. As a result, the researcher attempts to investigate the impact of a computer with a screen reader on writing skills of student with visual impairment.

Objective of the Study

To find out the effect of computer with screen reader on writing skill of student with visual impairment.

Research Question

What is the effect of using computer with screen reader on writing skill of students with visual impairment?

Review of Literature

Svensson et al., (2021) explored the effect of assistive technology on children with reading and writing challenges. The goal of the study was to find effect of assistive technology on children with severe reading impairment. The participants in this study were 149 students (53 females and 96 boys) in grades 4 and 8 at a Swedish primary school. They were then divided into two groups: the experimental and the control. For the pre-test and post-test, the researchers created a questionnaire. The experimental group was given 24 sessions of assistive technology training, whereas the control group was given standard care. The findings of the study show that using assistive technology has a positive impact on reading ability and helpful, especially for children with the most severe issues. Silman et al., (2017) investigated the process of visually impaired students receiving technology-assisted teaching, learning, and administration. The objective of the study was to investigate technology-aided teaching-learning and administrative processes for visually impaired students. The semi-structured interview method was used to collect data. Two interview schedules were developed, one for teachers and students and the other for the administrator. Data was collected and analyzed using a qualitative research technique.

Research Design

Because of the nature of the current study, experimental research is deemed the best method for achieving the study's goal. A single case pre-post- experimental design was used in this study. The study employs a single subject research design, which is commonly used to study an individual's behavioural change as a result of some treatment. The goal of single-subject experimental research is to determine the effects of a single intervention on a single person. The single subject research design strategy is the most scientifically valid method of making the best decision for visually impaired students. Personalization of data analysis is an important feature of single-subject experimental research. Studies with a single subject provide evidence of the efficacy of any type of intervention programme. If there is a change in an individual after the intervention, the treatment is effective. A single female student with visual impairment was taken as a sample for the study. Inclusion Criteria: The age is between 10 years old. Female student with blindness without additional disabilities. Having basic screen reading knowledge in computer. Having basic typing skills in English in computer. Tool for the Study: A tool is essential for gathering true and unbiased data from the sample of the study. A tool may either be developed by the researcher or adapted to the needs of the study. As there are no readymade tools for the purpose of the study, a systematic effort was made by the investigator to develop the tool. To achieve the objective of the present study, the researcher has designed a yes or no type questionnaire to find out the writing skills in students with visual impairment using a screen reader.

The Organization and Scoring Procedure of the Rating Scale

The forty-eight Dolch sight words listed below are used to assess the writing abilities of student with visual impairment. The questionnaire contained 48 items based on each word. The questionnaire has a maximum score of 48 and a minimum score of 0.

Table 1: List of Dolch Sight word- fifth grade

Afternoon	Already	Although
Beautiful	Carefully	Chance
Compare	Consider	Corner
Details	Determine	Difficult
Division	Electric	Entire
Equation	Everything	Experience
Factories	Finish	Guess
Happiness	Impossible	Machine
Material	Movement	Neither

Ought	Particular	Pattern
Prepared	Process	Produce
Rather	Silent	Speak
Substance	Suggest	Supply
Though	Thousand	Tomorrow
Underline	Understand	Weather
Whose	Wrong	Yet

Scoring Procedure: Before the intervention, words were dictated and pre-test score were marked. After 10 sessions of intervention post test scores were marked. Data Collection: The investigator collected the before and after the intervention. Stage 1-Pre-test: In the first stage, the investigator conducted a pre-test using a questionnaire to assess the writing skills of student with visual impairment using NVDA Screen reader. Stage 2-Intervention and Post-test: The second stage was the administration of intervention and post-test was conducted and scores were marked.

Analysis of data: Qualitative Analysis

Based on the objective of the study, qualitative analysis was done based on the performance in writing skills using graphical representation.

Results and Interpretation

What is the effect of using computer with screen reader on writing skill of student with visual impairment?

To find out the significant differences between pre and post-test scores among student with visual impairment, the investigator used the graphical representation of the data. Table 2 & graph 1 shows difference between pre and post test scores of the female student with visual impairment in writing skills.

Table 2: Writing skills of Student with Visual Impairment

Pre Test Score	Post Test 1	Post Test 2	Post Test 3
15	32	43	47

From the table 2 revealed that post-test scores are higher than pre-test scores, with a substantial difference in favour of post-test results. This shows that using computer with screen reader is very effective in selected female student with visual impairment to improve writing skills.

Conclusion

Technology has become ingrained in our daily lives. Through research, evidence of the role of technology in our daily lives has been discovered. Technology, in fact, has the potential to save lives. Today, communication, work, and education would be nearly impossible without technology. For students with visual impairments, embedded technology, such as screen reading software, paves the way for the development of writing skills. The study found that using a computer with a screen reader had a significant effect on writing ability in students with visual impairment.

References

- [1] Banat, S. (2007). The effect of a program based on the process approach and learning style on developing EFL writing skills among Jordanian secondary stage students. Unpublished Ph. D Thesis, Amman Arab University for Graduate Studies, Amman, Jordan.
- [2] Hunt, C. (2000). Therapeutic dimensions of autobiography in creative writing. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- [3] <https://sites.ed.gov/idea/about-idea/>

EFFECTIVENESS OF AUGMENTED REALITY TO ENHANCE CRITICAL THINKING OF STEM EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract

The study was made with an objective to experiment and explore the effectiveness of augmented reality-based STEM education on critical thinking of the students. The study adopted an experimental research design, wherein 42 samples were considered. For the study; Concept visualization, Concept perception, Concept correlation with the real world, Interactive, Concept inferential and interpretation were considered as study variables associated with critical thinking. The study indicated that both male and female respondents agree that the augmented reality helping them better visualize, perceive, interpret and correlate it with the real world than other conventional and traditional teaching methods in STEM education. Further, it was identified that Critical thinking of students is strongly and positively correlated with Concept visualization, Concept perception, Concept correlation with the real world, Interactive, Concept inferential and interpretation.

Keywords:*Augmented Reality, STEM Education, Critical Thinking.*

Introduction

Augmented Reality (AR) is an interactive experience of a real-world environment Designers create everything from audio to video visuals, from picture to Global Positioning System overlays to digital content, which acknowledges in actual-time to different in the user's environment, usually motion. AR is defined as an organization that satisfaction three basic features: a mixture of actual and video-virtual worlds, real-time communication, and accurate 3D recording of video and audio virtual and real objects. The above emotional information is either constructive (i.e., in combination with the natural environment), or destructive (i.e., obscuring the natural environment). In this way, developed reality changes one's current real-surroundings, while virtual reality completely transforms the user's real-world environment into a simulated one. For example, head-up displays on many fighter jets from the 1990s onwards show information about the aircraft's approach, direction, and speed, and only a few years later can they show which objects are in sight. A standard STEM program that focuses on math to help students acquire the skills needed to succeed in today's challenging world. These include solve complex problems, and promote advances in science and technology. Over the earlier decade, only a limited studies have sightseen reality (AR) technology that has evolved to engage with innovative and critical thinking in the field of academic research. Therefore, the use of augmented reality based learning was avoided and traditional teaching methodology was given more Importance. The AR system is based on five critical thinking skills; I.e. interpretation, evaluation with real world, rationalization, concept visualization and evaluation to training participants with critical thinking skills during the functioning of the organization. For the study, university students has been selected from which 42 participants (18-20 years old) from the first year to engage in the experiments. Tests include tests, intervention, and post-testing to explore the impact and learning effectiveness of using AR with critical thinking for STEM education among students.

Objectives of the Study

The study involves investigating whether the augmented reality enhance the critical thinking of the students pursuing STEM education. Further, the study explores important aspects of critical thinking that are stimulated during augmented reality-based STEM education.

Research Methodology

For the study, an experimental research design was adopted. Herein engineering class consisting of 42 students were considered. The study was conducted in the time frame of 2 months involving 5 faculties specialized in a STEM subject. One unit was taught through augmented reality and the response was collected after the assessment through subjects in STEM.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Analysis and Interpretation

The reliability statistics were measured using Cronbach's Alpha method to check the reliability of the construct named Critical Thinking.

Table No. – 1: Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics				
Cronbach's Alpha			N of Items	
0.813			5	
Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I have a better visualization of concept than in traditional and conventional learning method.	15.619	13.071	0.401	0.835
I noticed I have a better perceived quality of STEM education when teacher through Augmented reality	15.881	12.205	0.618	0.773
I could correlate STEM concept studied through Augmented reality and the real world, to make use it.	15.619	11.364	0.791	0.726
Unlike other methods Augmented reality is making me more interactive with the class and help me learn new concepts every day.	15.7619	9.454	0.759	0.724
The information delivered through augmented reality is stimulating my inferential and interpretation ability	15.5952	12.881	0.501	0.805

Source: (Primary data)

The estimated Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.813, which is greater than 0.7. Meaning the construct named Critical Thinking and all its associated items are reliable for conducting further research. Also, all the variables named; Visualization, Perception, Correlate, Interactive, inferential and interpretation when examined individually exhibited Cronbach's reliability score greater than 0.7 [Standard Value].

Table No. – 2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Rank
I have a better visualization of concept than in traditional and conventional learning method.	42	4	2
I noticed I have a better- perceived quality of STEM education when teacher through Augmented reality	42	3.7381	5
I could correlate STEM concept studied through Augmented reality and the real world, to make use it.	42	4	2
Unlike other methods Augmented reality is making me more interactive with the class and help me learn new concepts every day.	42	3.8571	4
The information delivered through augmented reality is stimulating my inferential and interpretation ability	42	4.0238	1

Source: (Primary data)

From the mean score rank analysis, it can be interpreted that, using Augmented reality-based STEM education helps students to better interpret, visualize and correlate STEM concepts with the real world. Mann-Whitney U test was carried to identify whether there is a significant difference in opinion among the male and female students who had undergone augmented reality-based STEM education. Herein the researcher had adopted Mann-Whitney U test because, the data was not normally distributed, and further the ordinal scale was used to measure the Critical thinking construct having a limited sample size of 42.

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Table No. – 3: Mann-Whitney U –Gender [Group] and Critical thinking [Construct]

Test Statistics	Mann-Whitney U	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	
I have a better visualization of concept than in traditional and conventional learning method.	180	-0.247	0.805	
I noticed I have a better- perceived quality of STEM education when teacher through Augmented reality	130.5	-1.76	0.078	
I could correlate STEM concept studied through Augmented reality and the real world, to make use it.	155	-0.969	0.333	
Unlike other methods Augmented reality is making me more interactive with the class and help me learn new concepts every day.	144	-1.286	0.198	
The information delivered through augmented reality is stimulating my inferential and interpretation ability	144	-1.323	0.186	
Mode Analysis				
		Valid	Missing	Mode
I have a better visualization of concept than in traditional and conventional learning method.		42	0	5
I noticed I have a better-perceived quality of STEM education when teacher through Augmented reality		42	0	4
I could correlate STEM concept studied through Augmented reality and real-world, to make use it.		42	0	4
Unlike other methods Augmented reality is making me more interactive with the class and help me learn new concepts everyday.		42	0	5
The information delivered through augmented reality is stimulating my inferential and interpretation ability		42	0	4

Source: (Primary data)

The estimated significance value is greater than 0.05, meaning the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore it can be interpreted that, there is no significant difference in opinion among the male and female students. From the mode value, it can be interpreted that, students strongly agree that augmented reality-based STEM education is interactive and helps in better visualization of the concept. The Spearman correlation was conducted because the considered dataset has variables whose scale is measured in ordinal further there was a limited sample size of 42.

Table No. – 4: Spearman's Correlation

Correlations - Spearman's rho						
		Concept visualization	Concept perception	Concept correlation with real world	Interactive	Concept inferential and interpretation
Concept visualization	Correlation Coefficient	1	.406**	.341*	0.077	-0.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	0.008	0.027	0.628	0.742
	N	42	42	42	42	42
Concept perception	Correlation Coefficient	.406**	1	.307*	.308*	.352*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.008	.	0.048	0.047	0.022
	N	42	42	42	42	42

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Concept correlation with real world	Correlation Coefficient	.341*	.307*	1	.581**	.692**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.027	0.048	.	0.000	0.000
	N	42	42	42	42	42
Interactive	Correlation Coefficient	0.077	.308*	.581**	1	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.628	0.047	0.000	.	0.004
	N	42	42	42	42	42
Concept inferential and interpretation	Correlation Coefficient	-0.052	.352*	.692**	.433**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.742	0.022	0.000	0.004	.
	N	42	42	42	42	42

Source: (primary data)

The estimated significance value for all variables was measured to be less than 0.05, meaning the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates, there is a significant relationship between every variable. From, the correlation coefficient value can be further interpreted that there is a significant positive relationship with every variable. Except for the variables Visualization with interactive and concept inferential & interpretation whose significance is greater than 0.05, meaning there is no significant relationship between the variables.

Table No. – 5: Spearman’s Correlation – Critical thinking & Study variables

Correlations - Spearman's rho		
		Critical Thinking
Concept visualization	Correlation Coefficient	.560**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	42
Concept perception	Correlation Coefficient	.629**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	42
Concept correlation with real world	Correlation Coefficient	.827**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	42
Interactive	Correlation Coefficient	.498**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001
	N	42
Concept inferential and interpretation	Correlation Coefficient	.697**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000
	N	42

Source: (Primary data)

The estimated significance value for all variables was measured to be less than 0.05, meaning the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates, there is a significant relationship between Concept visualization, Concept perception, Concept correlation with the real world, Interactive, Concept inferential and interpretation with critical thinking. From the correlation coefficient, it can be interpreted that the Concept correlation with the real world has a strong positive relationship between Critical thinking.

Findings and Discussion

The finding indicated that; Concept perception, Concept correlation with the real world, Interactive, Concept inferential and interpretation are variables associated with Critical thinking. Further, it can be well perceived that AR-based STEM education is helping both male and female students achieve Critical thinking significantly. Hereby AR-based STEM education has the potential to reduce absenteeism and increase interactive. Also, this kind of learning induces better concept learning and interpretation. Moreover, these learning methodologies are helping students apply their learned concept in real-world creating a useful application and implication, which is a soul motto of the teaching.

Conclusion

From the Cronbach's Alpha Statistics it was found that all the variables named; Concept visualization, Concept perception, Concept correlation with real-world, Interactive, Concept inferential and interpretation are reliable. Also, the study indicated that both male and female respondents agree that the augmented reality helps them better visualize, perceive, interpret and correlate it with the real world than other conventional and traditional teaching methods in STEM education.

References

- [1] Birt, J. C. (2017). Toward Future 'Mixed Reality' Learning Spaces For Steam Education. *Int.J. Innov. Sci. Math. Educ.*, 25.
- [2] Blecken, D. &. (2009). Augmented Reality. *Media: Asia's Media & Marketing Newspaper*, Retrieved from Business Source Premier Database., 1-5.
- [3] D. Cantor, B. J. (2012). *WebGL Beginner's Guide*. Packt Publishing.

HOLISTIC HEALTH AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The title “physical education” (PE) is the traditional taxonomy used to represent the education discipline. Health and physical education (HPE) is regarded to be an all-encompassing health-dimensional title that has been recently embraced by various education systems around the world. Hence, it can be argued that PE and HPE are often used interchangeably by educationalists, portraying a similar meaning and understanding. This can be regarded as internationally confusing, as historically PE and HPE have represented different and at times paradoxical discourses and ideologies. Amongst the ambiguity of which title to use, PE or HPE, new terms of branding such as “physical literacy” and “health literacy” have re/emerged. The purpose of this interpretivist study is to identify if associated terms used for the original PE label are a help or hindrance to practitioners? Participants were asked an open-ended question relating to PE nomenclatures. The data gathered were analysed and findings confirmed that practitioner confusion does exist. It is suggested that children are first and foremost “physically educated”; therefore a strong, clear and comprehensive grounding in quality PE is essential for teachers and students.

Introduction

Exploration of the past reveals that physical education (PE) has been influenced by two philosophies: (1) body viewed as an object; and (2) the view of the whole person; body, mind, spirit and well-being. It is important to understand these two philosophical influences in recognition that PE is socially constructed and subsequently semantics have evolved over time. Literature suggests that on occasions throughout history, PE has been responsible for schooling the body, where the body is viewed as an object. The body as an object occurs “in a society when man [and woman] has gained the capacity of looking at his [or her] own body as if it were a thing” (Broekhoff, 1972, p. 88). This concept is described by Kirk as a “useful and controlled body, one which is appropriately skilled with the capacities to meet the standards of acceptable social behaviour of any particular society and to make a productive contribution within the economic system” (Kirk, 1993, p. 13). Companion PE discourses that have influenced this philosophy include military, scientific, health and sporting, which portray ideologies which include sexism, elitism, healthism, individualism and mesomorphism (Colquhoun, 1991, 1992; Hickey, 1995; Kirk, 1992; Kirk & Twigg, 1993; Scraton, 1990; Tinning, 1990; Tinning & Fitzclarence, 1992; Tinning, Kirk, & Evans, 1993). Wherein, students acquire knowledge and attitudes unintentionally while in the school environment (Kirk, 1992). Such ideologies are regarded as problematic as they give false messages (Kirk, 1992). The introduction of the sociocultural approach saw a philosophical shift using a “holistic” discourse in PE. This holistic view was influenced by an inclusive ideology and in some regions of the world was relabelled HPE. This shift has occurred on numerous occasions throughout history, but most recently began as a complex counter discourse to those associated with the “body as object” philosophy. The whole child view was “informed by critical pedagogues and pedagogy in Australia, the United Kingdom and New Zealand in the 1980s and 1990s” (Cliff, Wright, & Clarke, 2009, p. 165). This holistic discourse had important implications for PE teachers and students, “because its attention to social and cultural influences on health put it in opposition to notions which locate responsibility for health almost solely in the individual and their decisions”. This discourse changed perception of the body as a separate object, to that of the “whole person”; body, mind, spirit and well-being, along with their social and cultural context. Whitehead (2010) refers to this shift in PE in philosophical terms as “dualism” and “monism”, respectively, but prefers to use the word “literacy” rather than “education”.

Literature Review

A glance through history illustrates that from the dawn of civilisation primitive man had to be very physically active to survive (Duncan & Watson, 1960). During ancient times, PE was given considerable emphasis by the Spartans, where PE was state regulated, age determined and involved similar experiences for men and women, boys and girls (Phillips & Roper, 2006). However, PE has been philosophically associated with more than just the physical dimension. Similar to the Athenians, the Romans recognised the benefits of physical education for quality of life, but the Romans preferred milder forms of exercise (Phillips & Roper, 2006). It can be argued that the purpose of PE for the Athenians and Romans during this ancient time was similar to HPE

today, to educate the mind and the body embedded within all dimensions of health: In Health and Physical Education students develop the knowledge, understanding and skills to support them to be resilient, to develop a strong sense of self, to build and maintain satisfying relationships, to make health-enhancing decisions in relation to their health and physical activity participation, and to develop health literacy competencies in order to enhance their own and others' health and wellbeing. (Australian Curriculum, Assessment & Reporting Authority (ACARA), 2012, p. 2). Whipp encapsulates the historical and present implications of the HPE ideal closely associated with "wellbeing"; a state of feeling good about ourselves (Commonwealth of Australia, 2014). In the past, the Greek ideal; "Mens sano in corpore sano", stressed the importance of having a healthy mind within a healthy body. For while only a few curriculum documents "explicitly acknowledge a socio-cultural perspective many, if not most, incorporate aspects of a socio-cultural perspective in their learning goals and content". The process of objectifying the body was evident in the second-century AD when Galen opened the human body. Galen didn't believe he saw anything, but he only saw what he believed (Kirk, 1993). Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519) was the first to give an accurate description of the muscles and their functions, which was not published until the end of the eighteenth century (Broekhoff, 1972).

Methodology

The purpose of this study was to investigate if issues raised in literature regarding uncertainty and confusion about associated PE terms, exists amongst practitioners. This interpretivist study was positioned within a constructionist paradigm. This theoretical framework is most appropriate for this study considering that understanding of the PE field, its clarity and success of policy implementation ultimately depends on teachers and students (Gardner & Williamson, 1999). The participants shared their experiences and perspectives within their context, which are never wrong. This was important as the implementation of curriculum, policies and PE terms adopted differ between nations and states. The interpretive perspective assumes that there is change and that we live in an ever-changing world (Glesne, 1999). Emphasis is placed on the change and development of individuals, groups and societies (Sarantakos, 1998). This is most suitable given the various discourses, ideologies and philosophies that have influenced the PE field over the years. With regards to practitioner's clarity of the PE terms, it is envisaged that there will be both positive and negative outcomes. This assumption is based on the personal experiences of the researcher, who in "qualitative research is often the primary instrument for data collection and analysis".

Findings and Discussion

An elementary [primary] teacher from New Jersey on the eastern region of the US, who we will refer to as Robert, shared "I don't think they are separate now" and suggests that "If time is not a factor it would be smart to combine both because one is not independent of the other". This evidences the holistic HPE philosophy, but Robert adds; "The biggest problem is time. We barely have time to teach Physical education standards. How are we going to add health standards to an already overloaded program?" Revealing that the HPE ideal is not the case in practice where PE and health standards are implemented separately. Rebecca, also an elementary teacher in a school located in Washington in North West of the US comments; "I like the concept of HPE as one learning area. I am a big believer in educating the 'whole child' and try to include various aspects of health education in my teaching at the elementary level. My District does not have a PE curriculum, we all wing it on our own". Rebecca shares that she connects health but it would appear it is at PE's expense.

What is the Structure for PE/HPE Implementation?

Within the PE field in the US states it appears that time was the major barrier for teachers. As Robert shared; "The biggest problem is time. We barely have time to teach Physical education standards. How are we going to add health standards to an already overloaded program?" Other barriers included a lack of either a health curriculum (Ruth) or physical education curriculum (Rebecca), and also professional development (Lucy). This often resulted in the prioritisation of PE but as Rebecca from Washington shared, health is at times taught at the expense of PE. Kate spoke of her disbelief in the HPE ideal because of the practical barriers. The overwhelming response was that the curriculum, classes and often teachers within various states were segregated when it comes to "health" and "PE". Another barrier was teacher preparation, as Ruth shares; "creating a HPE titled position, although a good idea perhaps, could be truly burdensome to the PE teacher who has limited time with their students as it is in most instances. Proper training is a must since most PE majors don't really focus on Health unless they are striving for a separate certification". The school-based example promoted by a university academic was backed by a research grant which would often enable the necessary time. However, he did advocate

HPE leadership, adopting clear communication and underpinned by a “whole school” approach (Lynch, 2015a).

How do Practitioners Differentiate between PE Terms?

The main terms discussed were PE and HPE. The third term mentioned was PL which was written into the standards for PE. This clarified that PL was a view of PE rather than a separate concept. PE was often discussed as though it represented only the physical dimension. HPE was referred to as the development of the whole child and all health dimensions. Hence, PE and HPE were referred to as different concepts. As Richard summarised; “We only have one focus but it isn’t health or PE, it’s the whole child”. In this sense, PE does appear to have been contained only to represent the physical dimension, which may be related to “body as object” philosophy, consisting of problematic discourses and ideologies embedded within (Kirk, 1993). The Athenians and Romans perceived PE within the “holistic” philosophy, as has organisations such as ICHPER-SD in the latter half of the twentieth century. Ruth and Lucy evidenced a strong understanding of the term holistic HPE and what it looked like in practice, despite having separate health teacher and PE teacher job titles. They both (along with Barry) spoke of connecting the curriculum or integrating which has been recommended for the sociocultural perspective (Cliff et al., 2009). However, most practitioners demonstrated a concoction of paradoxical terms, discourses, ideologies and philosophies.

Conclusion

This study gathered empirical data from practitioners to investigate their thoughts on the various labels for PE and how they appear in practice. Data were analysed using Wellington’s (2000) simplified version of the “constant comparative method for analysing qualitative data” (Figure 1). The terms today, PE and HPE (and to a less degree “physical literacy” and “health literacy”) are often used interchangeably. The data indicate that if the traditionally named term for the field, PE is used without reference to health, HPE or PL then it portrays a “body as object” philosophy, whether it does or not. Hence, while PE has traditionally represented physicality that enhances all dimensions of health, data and literature indicates that it no longer means this for practitioners. It only represents the physical dimension and even suggests that it has poor quality connotations. This appears to be a direct result of using a number of labels to represent PE.

References

- [1] Kirk, D. (1992). Physical education, discourse, and ideology: Bringing the hidden curriculum into view. *The body schooling and culture—monograph*. Geelong: Deakin University Press.
- [2] Kirk, D. (2013). Educational value and models-based practice in physical education. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*.
- [3] Kirk, D., & Macdonald, D. (1998). The physical activity profession in process: Unity, diversity and the Australian council for health, physical education and recreation 1970–1997. *Sporting Traditions*.
- [4] Kumar, R. (2005). *Research methodology* (2nd ed.). Frenchs Forest: Pearson Education.
- [5] Lynch, T. (2015b). Health and physical education (HPE): Implementation in primary schools. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 70, 88–100.
- [6] Lynch, T. (2015c). Investigating children’s spiritual experiences through the health and physical education (HPE) learning area in Australian schools. *Journal of Religion and Health*.
- [7] Corbin, C. (2016). Implications of physical literacy for research and practice: A commentary. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*.
- [8] Crawford, R. (1980). Healthism and the medicalization of everyday life. *International Journal of Health Services*.
- [9] Tinning, R., Kirk, D., & Evans, J. (1993). Healthism and daily physical education.

NEED FOR HOLISTIC EDUCATION IN THE POST-PANDEMIC SITUATION

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Abstract

Covid-19 did not just pose a health challenge but brought in a bigger mental challenge for the whole world including students, even the young students' toddlers and tweens. The need for developing social skills, emotional and adversity quotient has hence turned out to be most important, even beyond subject knowledge. The Holistic Education system that shows to promote philosophical orientation along with life skills and an introspective approach among students, is needed much more, than could have been identified before the onset of the pandemic. The present article has identified the various pillars of holistic education and its necessity in the post-covid situation. A plethora of behavioural challenges identified among students post the pandemic can be said to be managed by Holistic Education. The same has been detailed in the paper and need to utilise the same by all schools across the country or rather the world even in the rural areas has been stressed upon. The paper has tried to bring out the need of the hour to start implementing the concept in practical usage across the country to reap the benefits of a happy and healthy budding generation.

Introduction

Stress, Depression, Anxiety, Obesity, Nosophobia have turned out to be buzz words these days. Life has yet not returned completely to normal for anyone, like it was before Covid-19 pandemic. And for many it will never return to. When we say anyone, we do consider the vulnerable age groups like toddlers and tweens too. But education is a must and hence should go on at its best. All said and done, the new concept of holistic education has been seen to be quite impactful when considered its nature of overall development (Andishehjo, 2020). The present paper would consider the concept of Holistic Education in the light of the present situation and its pressing demands. In the course of the discussion the mitigating capabilities of Holistic Education on the prominent challenges would be checked upon.

Concept of Holistic Education and its Emerging Trends Post Covid-19

The foundation of holistic education is a learning concept that benefits students, teachers, schools, and communities in several ways (Mahmoudi, Jafari, Hasan, & Nasrabadi, 2012). The students are given the power to enhance their academic performance and acquire the life skills required to embark on a prosperous professional journey. The approach promotes a mix of philosophical orientations combined with well-designed pedagogies with an aim of holistic development in terms of the physical, social, emotional, aesthetic, and emotional development of the student (Venugopal, 2009). The education system being talked about here has proved to be supportive in developing: According to the Learning Policy Institute (Melnick, et al., 2020), children's brain development is proper when they feel both physically and emotionally safe and linked to others. Enhanced Mental and Emotional Well-Being: Students have a better chance of emerging from supportive environments where social and emotional learning is prioritized alongside academics with self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of purpose and social accountability. Greater Capability to Solve Problems: The students who are given real-world problems to solve in their communities develop great critical-thinking abilities (Miseliunaite, Kliziene, & Cibulskas, 2022). These practical assignments teach students abilities that they might use in their adult employment, like how to collect, evaluate, and report data and how to work with others.

Challenges Posed Beyond the Pandemic

It was not just a situation of health challenge; it was something far bigger and deeper. The entire population did not get directly contract the virus, but every individual felt the repercussions in some or the other way. The mental impact was indeed the biggest challenge. Major population sets contracted nosophobia, an ongoing fear of contracting deadly diseases. The social seclusion brought in various behavioral challenges. Loss of near and dear ones brought in adversity crisis situations for people (Plakhotnik, et al., 2021).

Challenges Faced after Covid

The COVID-19 epidemic has had multiple effects on students, including risks to their health and the health of their families, school closures, a shift to online learning, a lengthy tenure of physical separation from school, teachers, and friends, and finally the problem of going back to school in the fall of 2020. There has been much argument regarding the "second wave" of mental health crises, particularly for school-aged children and adolescents, as detrimental as the physical health repercussions of a worldwide pandemic are (Chaturvedi K, 2020). However, only just a few studies have questioned students about their experiences during the pandemic. Students expressed mild and equal worry about their health, on being isolated from their families, and continuing to interact with others.

Holistic Education – Need of the Hour

An approach to pedagogy known as holistic education can suit the requirements of all sorts of students, can bring satisfaction and joy to instructors, and can produce future citizens who will offer concern and mindfulness for others, for their communities, and for the environment. Both environmental education and global education, which are similarly founded on the ideas of interdependence and connectedness, are compatible with them (Ebrahim Jafari, 2012). Holistic education aims to build a society where we live in peace with our surroundings based on this interdependent perspective. It disapproves of consumerism as the prevalent way of life in contemporary culture. Instead, it strives for an education that is founded on the most fundamental truths about life and the natural world. The goal of holistic education is:

Human Development Education

The main goal of education is to foster the natural capacities for human development. Schools must be environments that support each student's whole growth. Learning necessitates the strengthening of ties to oneself, family, friends, the larger community, the earth, and the cosmos.

Recognizing Students as Unique Beings

Every learner is different, creative by nature, and has different requirements and abilities. This entails accepting individual differences and encouraging tolerance, respect, and an awareness of human uniqueness in each pupil. Each person has innate creativity and a unique personality.

The Primary Function of Experience

Learning is essentially experienced, and education is a matter of experience. Learning is an interactive, multimodal interaction between a person and the outside world; it gives the learner power and reveals the depth of the world's meaning. Experience is fluid and constantly expanding. The above specified details of how Holistic Education works, show a relatedness towards the pressing need of changes of the hour. These are quite in line to what we need to offer as part of education at this point of time over the traditional style of just imparting knowledge with an aim to higher scores.

Conclusion

The Indian education system though very well adopted to the new virtual mode, large set of rural population lost years on, as internet was neither a choice nor chance for them. Typical figures of stress struck population, suicidal incidents, lifestyle disorders like obesity, slip disks, behavioral aggression, sleep disorders, attention disorders, food cravings as well as hypertension has not only posed a challenge towards their overall well-being, but full families are struggling the aftermaths of pandemic, which calls for more support in these fortes as part of education.

Reference

- [1] Chaturvedi K, V. D. (2020, Dec 25). Behavioural aspects after covid:COVID-19 and its impact on education, social life and mental health of students: A survey. PubMed. Retrieved Jan 16, 2023
- [2] Ebrahim Jafari, H. A. (2012, May 9). Pillars of holistic education-Holistic Education: An Approach for 21 Century. International Education Studies, 5(3).
- [3] Mahmoudi, S., Jafari, E., Hasan, A., & Nasrabadi. (2012, April). Holistic Education: An Approach for 21 Century. International Educational Studies, 5(3). Retrieved Jan 22, 2023

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES FOLLOWED BY COLLEGE STUDENTS WHILE WASHING REUSABLE CLOTH FACEMASK AGAINST CORONA VIRUS

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic, also known as the Coronavirus pandemic, originally discovered in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. There were attempts to contain it, but they were unsuccessful, allowing it to spread to other parts of the globe. The Present study mainly aimed to assess the practices followed by college students while washing reusable cloth facemask against Corona virus. A sample of 200 students (100 boys and 100 girls) were randomly selected from MPUAT, Udaipur. The results revealed that, students have good knowledge regarding safe practices to be followed while disposing facemask, while most of the students preferred hand wash technique, scrubbing with detergents and majority washed their facemask after every single use worn against corona virus. Significant difference was found between boys and girls habit of cleaning hands with soap water/sanitizer before touching mask.

Keywords: COVID-19, Knowledge, Facemasks, Disposal Practices, College Students

Introduction

The Coronavirus Pandemic, referred to as Covid-19, was first identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. There were attempts to contain it, but they were unsuccessful, allowing it to spread to other parts of the globe. Following the Covid-19 prevention recommendations provided by the WHO, such as keeping a distance of at least one meter from people, donning a mask that fits properly, regularly washing or sanitizing hands, getting immunized, staying at home, isolating from others if the symptoms are noticed in person, and adhering to hygiene practices like regularly disinfecting or cleaning the most touched areas like faucet handles, mobiles, door knobs, etc., prevents a person from getting sick. The efficiency of masks varies; N95 masks offer the highest defense, followed by medical and KN95 masks, and cloth masks provide less security (Chughtai et al., 2020). But even cloth masks, which come in a range of fabric types and sizes, provide users with a sizable amount of protection from particles carrying the Covid-19 virus. Positive attitudes regarding facemasks increase a person's likelihood of understanding their advantages and increasing their propensity to buy masks (Tran, 2021). For cloth or disposable masks, the CDC advises untying the straps, folding the outside corner inside, and placing the mask in a plastic bag until it can be washed, depending on whether it is dirty or wet, or whether it is dry and clean (such a paper bag or mesh fabric bag). When a cloth mask becomes filthy or dirty, it should be washed right away and dried for at least five hours in the sun. Once any masks have been taken off, wash or sterilize hands.

Objective

To assess the Knowledge and practices followed by college students while washing reusable cloth facemask against Corona virus

Methodology

200 college students of which 100 boys and 100 girls were selected from MPUAT Colleges. Random sampling technique was used for the selection of sample. A self- People with favorable attitude toward facemasks are more likely to realize the benefits of masks and be more willing to engage in mask purchases. A complete assessment of both internal and external resources that facilitate acting on the impulse to purchase items is known as perceived behavioral control structured questionnaire was developed to assess the knowledge and practices followed by college students while washing reusable cloth facemask against Corona virus. Four point scoring scale was used for the responses i.e., 4 for always, 3 for sometimes, 2 for Rarely and 1 for Never. Frequency and Percentage distribution was calculated and Chi-square test was used to know the difference of student's habits/practices followed by college students while washing reusable cloth facemask against Corona virus

Results

Knowledge and Practice Level in Safely Disposing a Used Facemask

The data in the table 1 shows that majority of students from both boys and girls group i.e., in overall 74% boys and 89% girls rated their knowledge and practice level in safely disposing a used facemask was good to very good

Table 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of students based on knowledge and practice level in safely disposing a used facemask

S.No.	Knowledge Level	Boys, n=100		Girls, n=100	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Very poor	1	1	0	0
2	Poor	5	5	1	1
3	Average	20	20	10	10
4	Good	57	57	48	48
5	Very good	17	17	41	41

Frequency of Disinfecting Facemasks

Table 2 Frequency and percentage distribution of students based on how frequently the used masks was disinfected

S. No.	Preference	Boys, n=100		Girls, n=100	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1	Only when appears to be dirty/soiled	24	24	7	7
2	After using more than 3 times	26	26	14	14
3	After using 2 times	14	14	19	19
4	After every single use	19	19	44	44
5	I don't use reusable masks	17	17	16	16
	Total	100	100	100	100

26% of boys stated that they washed their masks after using for more than 3 times, followed by 24%, washed when mask appeared to be dirty or soiled, 14%-boys washed after using for 2 times and, only 17% stated that they washed their masks after every single use,, while 17% reported that they didn't use reusable masks. While 44% girls have washed their facemask after every single use followed by 19% washed after using it for 2 times,14% washed after using for more than 3 times.

Method/ technique followed to wash facemasks

Table 3 Frequency and percentage distribution of students based on method/ technique followed to wash facemask (Multiple responses were accepted from students)

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S.No.	Method/ technique followed	Boys, n=100		Girls, n=100	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Boiling for 5-10 min	21	21	26	26
2	Machine wash	32	32	19	19
3	Scrubbing with detergents	42	42	59	59
4	Kneading & squeezing	10	10	28	28
5	Just rinsing under water and drying	42	42	25	25

According to the data in table 3, an equal percentage of boys - 42% scrubbed their masks with detergents or simply rinsed under water and dried, 32% machine washed their masks, 28% kneaded and squeezed their masks, 26% and 25% boiled their masks for 5-10 minutes and rinsed under water and allowed.

Table 4 Frequency and percentage distribution of students based on steps followed while washing reusable cloth facemask

S.No.	Steps while washing reusable cloth masks	Always		Some times		Rarely		Never		Total	Chi-Square Value
		Boys f (%)	Girls f (%)	Boys f (%)	Girls f (%)	Boys f (%)	Girls f (%)	Boys f (%)	Girls f (%)		
1	Cleaning hands with soap water/sanitizer before touching mask	26	48	41	36	28	11	5	5	200	14.275*
2	Removing the mask by holding ear cords/straps	52	51	36	36	7	8	5	5	200	0.076 NS
3	Putting used mask in paper bag and leaving it in a warm place for at least 2 days so it won't be infectious	18	28	24	34	27	20	31	18	200	7.589 NS
4	Presoaking facemask in hot water for 5-10 min before washing	30	36	17	37	21	21	32	6	200	5.319 NS
5	Using bleach to disinfect facemask	29	31	28	37	18	16	25	16	200	3.406 NS
6	Letting facemask dry in sunlight for more than 5 hours after Washing	21	31	34	36	23	13	22	20	200	4.853 NS
7	Wearing disposable gloves while washing facemask	11	22	20	31	21	17	48	30	200	4.852 NS

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8	Washing facemask along with daily laundry	47	49	37	35	6	11	10	5	200	3.234 NS
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*5% level of significance

48% of girls and 26% of boys have agreed that they have always cleaned their hands with soap water/sanitizer before touching mask, 52% and 51% of boys and girls respectively have agreed that they have always removed their mask by holding ear cords/straps. 29% of boys and 31% of girls always used bleach to disinfect their used facemask, 21% of boys and 31% of girls have always let facemask dry in sunlight for more than 5 hours after washing, only 11% boys and 22% girls have always wore disposable gloves while washing facemask and 47% boys and 49% girls have always washed their facemask along with daily laundry.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that students have good knowledge related to practices to be followed while washing reusable cloth facemask against Corona virus, but the safety practices were not so well followed by students. Majority preferred hand wash technique, scrubbing with detergents and majority washed their facemask after every single use worn against corona virus. Significant difference was found between boys and girls habit of cleaning hands with soap water/sanitizer before touching mask.

References

- [1] https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_1
- [2] <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/advice-for-public>
- [3] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Face_masks_during_the_COVID-19_pandemic
- [4] <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/prevent-getting-sick/about-face-coverings.html>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION THROUGH LIFE SKILLS WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract

This article emphasizes that provision of outcome based education through implementing life skill and special emphasis on critical thinking. The education provides various outcomes to the learners based on the expected outcomes prescribed in the content. The real outcome of the education with special attention to life skills and other skills related to the individual who will be succeeded their life. Especially critical thinking is plays major role for individual to carry out their life journey in the peaceful way. The development of critical thinking takes various ways. However, the outcome based education provides strong foundation to enhance the critical thinking among learners. The life skill education plays major contribution to promote different perception on learners who will precede life with successful way. The development of life skill education through outcome based education take place long time effectiveness in the minds of the learners to perform their task without the mental struggle. The developments of life skill with special emphasis on critical thinking among students have positive inspiration among them to achieve the goals. This article also highlights the significance of provision to outcome based education through implementing life skill education with special emphasis on critical thinking.

Keywords: *Outcome Based Education, Life Skills, Critical Thinking*

Introduction

Outcome-based education or outcomes-based education (OBE) is an educational theory that bases each part of an educational system around goals (outcomes). By the end of the educational experience, each student should have achieved the goal. There is no single specified style of teaching or assessment in OBE; instead, classes, opportunities, and assessments should all help students achieve the specified outcomes. The role of the faculty adapts into instructor, trainer, facilitator, and/or mentor based on the outcomes targeted. Outcome-based methods have been adopted in education systems around the world, at multiple levels. OBE can primarily be distinguished from traditional education method by the way it incorporates three elements: theory of education, a systematic structure for education, and a specific approach to instructional practice. It organizes the entire educational system towards what are considered essential for the learners to successfully do at the end of their learning experiences. In this model, the term "outcome" is the core concept and sometimes used interchangeably with the terms "competency", "standards", "benchmarks", and "attainment targets". OBE also uses the same methodology formally and informally adopted in actual workplace to achieve outcomes. It focuses on the following skills when developing curricula and outcomes the life skill of critical thinking.

Life Skill Education-A Glance

Life skills are a set of abilities, attitudes and socio-emotional competencies that enable individuals to learn, make informed decisions and exercise rights to lead a healthy and productive life and subsequently become agents of change. Life skills promote mental well-being and competence in young people¹ as they face the realities of life. These skills support the development of foundational skills such as literacy, numeracy, digital skills and can also be utilized in several areas, such as gender equality in education, environmental education, peace education or education for development, livelihood and income generation, and for positive health promotion among others. Life skills empower young people to take positive action to participate in their communities, engage in continuous learning, protect them and promote health and positive social relationships.

Importance of Critical Thinking in Education

The first mention of critical thinking was documented in the teaching of Socrates, recorded by Plato. Critical thinking occurs when a person analyzes, evaluates, and interprets information and then applies ingenious thought to form a judgment. Critical thinkers typically are self-evaluators, problem solvers, and clear analysts, open to others' ideas, cautious-they think before acting, open-minded, good listeners, and eager to take on challenges. A critical thinker is someone who thinks actively and interacts constantly with the world. Critical

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thinking can be developed in students by helping them construct their thoughts after analyzing, interpreting, and examining information. However, this strategy was a shortcoming in earlier education systems. Previously, teachers and mentors believed that pure fact-based knowledge gained from books and lessons allowed students to excel in life. However, this approach has taken a major shift in today's education system. Information travels much faster nowadays with advancements in technology, thus changing the way that students learn and explore the world. However, misrepresentation, false information, and inaccurate data also travel at the same speed. This is where critical thinking plays a major role. Analyzing all information critically and then solving problems and making decisions is the main purpose of education, achieved well through critical thinking skills taught in the classroom.

Advantage of Outcome Based Education

The outcome-based education imparts thinking skills and engages students more actively. When the student creates a product is much more meaningful than answers on a test or paper pencil evaluation. Outcome-based education (when done right) provides learning more similar to real-world applications and real-world problem solving.

Clarity in Concept: The emphasis on outcomes creates a clear anticipation of what needs to be inculcated and proficient by the end of the course or Programme. Students will get to know what is expected of them and teachers will understand what they need to teach during the course and Programme. Clarity is essential besides years of schooling and when teaching is accomplished as a team. Clarity helps each learner to have a clear understanding of what needs to be accomplished in each class, or at each level and pre-defined standard building students' progress. The people who are delineation and planning the curriculum objectives are expected to work once the outcome has been decided and delimited. The curriculum frame worker needs to determine what knowledge and skills will be required to arrive at the outcome.

Flexibility in Choice of Contents: Any method can be chosen to teach a student according to the learning style and ability to learn. OBE does not limit the teachers to teach using a specific method and gives to freedom to adopt customized strategies. OBE is a holistic and modern student-centered learning model and strategies. Teachers are meant to guide, mentor, facilitate and help the students master the material using either approach.

Students Voluntary Involvement learning: Student involvement in the classroom is a key part and it is inevitable of OBE. Students are expected to do self-motivated and self-engaged in learning so that they attain a full understanding of the material and core concept. It increases student involvement and allows students to feel responsible for their own learning. On the other hand, the parents and societies are indirect and moral helper for students learning outcomes.

Conclusion

This present article concludes that outcome based education through life skill with special emphasis on critical thinking plays a major role for determining the stability of students to success their life and career. The stake holders of education should give priority for outcome based education on inclusion of life skill education and also develop the critical thinking for the students to become a successful man in the life and career. There are more opportunities are available in the context of education to bring the different changes in the outcomes of students in the specific course they are studying. A lot of thought requires to be given on how to bring in life skills education into the mainstream curriculum in getting outcome based education with improving critical thinking among the future students.

References

- [1] Abbhilash, M. (2018). Things You Need To Know About Outcome-Based Education In India. 4 Things You Need To Know About Outcome-Based Education In India. Retrieved from <https://www.myclassroom.com/blog/4-things-to-know-about-outcome-based-education/>
- [2] Spady, L., And, W. & Marshall, K. (1991). Beyond Traditional Outcome-Based Education. *Beyond Traditional Outcome-Based Education* 2, 67–72.

EDUCATIONAL RIGHTS OF THE FEMALE GENDER IN ISLAM: OBLIGATION OR PROHIBITION

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Abstract

From antiquity, women were marginalized and treated unfairly in many ways, along with being denied educational rights. The female sex had not initially encouraged to pursue regular education until the latter half of the twentieth century. Although in the modern age, we live now in, several rights that Islam gives to females, particularly educational rights were refused. As per Islamic teachings, it is compulsory to acquire knowledge for all Muslims regardless of their sex. Unfortunately, several communities and religious faiths have a widespread perception regarding Islam that it constrains women from educational opportunities. The present study will analyze the educational status of the female gender in Islam and also, figure out the current educational status of Muslims. In this context, the basic sources of Islam will be used to figure out the educational status of the female gender.

Keywords: *Education, Rights, Female, Obligation.*

Introduction

Every individual has a basic right to receive an education, which serves as a cornerstone to prosperity and financial improvement around the globe. In 1948, the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” declared the right to education as a human right. Although, it was recognized as a basic requirement for a long time because it empowers human beings to identify their real God-given capacity. Moreover, at the beginning of the 21st century, “Education For All” (EFA), universal allegiance was made to grant basic quality education to all people irrespective of their sex and age, with the purpose of eradicating gender inequalities in education from the basic to the secondary level. The Millennium development goals have considered education among the basic requirement just after food and shelter. Islamic teachings have considered knowledge as a necessary requirement for both males and females. Seeking knowledge is an act of worship in Islam. It is a highly appreciated act that if a person dies on the path of knowledge, he or she will enter paradise. Unfortunately, a huge gap is evident between the practice of Muslims and Islamic guidelines.

Female Education Rights: Islamic Standpoint

This section will be discussed under two sub-sections, i.e., knowledge seeking in Islam, and current global education attainment of Muslims.

Knowledge Seeking in Islam

The first revelation of the Qur’an was a commandment of reading, which states:

“Read: In the name of thy Lord Who createth, Createth man from a clot. Read: And thy Lord is the Most Bounteous, Who teacheth by the pen, Teacheth man that which he knew not,”

A general rule regarding Islamic principles suggests that when a divine order is made, no matter if the language used is masculine, the female sex is included in that divine order. Now coming to the first commandment i.e., “Iqra”, Abdullah Yusuf Ali states that “The Arabic word for “teach” and “knowledge are from the same root. it is impossible to produce in a Translation the complete orchestral harmony of the words for “read”, “teach”, “pen” (which implies reading, writing, books, study, research), “knowledge” (including science, self knowing, spiritual understanding), and “proclaim”, an alternative meaning of the word for “to read”. Thus, the concept of knowledge in Islam is not limited to religious education rather it includes all aspects of knowledge that human beings can acquire. Also, God “teacheth by the pen”. No doubt pen (*Qalam*) is a powerful weapon in the transmission and preservation of knowledge. Apart from reading and pen, God says in another place regarding writing:

“O ye who believe! When ye contract a debt for a fixed term, record it in writing. Let a scribe record it in writing between you in (terms of) equity. No scribe should refuse to write as Allah hath taught him, so let him write, ...”

In this above verse, it is clear that “writing” is a gift from God. It is actually who taught humanity the skill of writing. Thus, reading, pen, and writing are the foundational tools for acquiring knowledge. In addition,

God taught the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be on him) to ask Him the following words:

“... and say: My Lord increase me in knowledge”.

Moreover, the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be on him) has said regarding knowledge-seeking:

“Seeking knowledge is a duty upon every Muslim, ...”

Thus, Islamic principles suggest that seeking knowledge is an obligation upon both males and females irrespective of their age. Another famous tradition in which Aisha (may Allah be pleased with her), the wife of Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be on him) said that “How good are the women of Ansar (helpers) that their shyness does not prevent them from learning religion.” This, tradition also suggests that shyness should be a barrier while acquiring knowledge and asking questions in order to get an education and follow the same have been appreciated in it. Finally, the Islamic concept of education is not limited to religion but it includes all aspects of knowledge which are beneficial for humanity.

Current Global Education Attainment of Muslims

Observations indicate that non-Muslim females are much more educated than Muslim females. In the global gender gap index of 2022, compiled by the World Economic Forum. A survey of one hundred forty-six countries was carried out, of which twenty-nine were Muslims. Only six Muslim countries have found a place among the top fifties of the global gender gap index in education attainment, these include Kazakhstan, Albania, Kuwait, Brunei Darussalam, UAE, and Kyrgyz. None of these six countries have a lower economy. Now the question rises here, is it religion or economy that creates a hindrance in the educational attainment of Muslim females? Pew Research Center observes that “economics, not religion, is the key factor limiting the education of Muslim women”. In addition, the World Economic Forum report suggests that “on average, high-income and middle-income economies have an Educational Attainment parity score of 99%, compared to 95% of lower-middle income and 81% of low-income economies”.

Constraints in Female Education Among Muslims

Is the economy alone responsible for constraining Muslim females from seeking knowledge? No, because there are other cultural and regional problems within Muslim communities few of them are: Uneducated families: Some Muslim families are uneducated and they did not allow their children to get an education, they follow their tradition, which is itself against the teachings of Islam. No economic responsibilities: A misconception among Muslims is that they thought male individuals must get an education because of their family’s responsible, unlike females who are not bound to earn, due to which their education is considered optional, unlike the Islamic teaching where it is an obligation upon both male and female.

Conclusion

The religion of Islam prohibits not females from acquiring knowledge, rather it laid great stress on knowledge acquisition. Islam had made knowledge-seeking an obligation instead of optional, how come would it prevent women from education when it has made its acquisition a duty for both males and females? Although there are reasons for the backwardness of female education, like economic limitations as well as traditional and cultural misconceptions, that drew them away from acquiring knowledge. Let us conclude with the statement of Dr. Yousef bin Ahmed Al-Othaimen, secretary of OIC, he says: “Education is the only way to empower them [girls], improve their status, ensure their participation in the development of their respective societies, and activate their role to be able to take responsibility for future generations.”

References

- [1] All the Quranic references are taken from “THE MEANINGS OF The Glorious Koran: AN EXPLANATORY TRANSLATION” Marmaduke Pickthall.
- [2] The Qur’an 96: 1-5.
- [3] Alavi, Hamid. Reza. (2008). Nearness to God: A perspective on Islamic education. Religious Education, Vol. 103, no. 1, pp 5-21. doi:10.1080/00344080701807361
- [4] Ali, A. Yusuf. (1997). THE GLORIOUS QUR’AN: Translation and Commentary, 2nd Edition. USA: American Trust Publications. P, 1761.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION CHALLENGES

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Abstract

An education system that includes all students, and welcomes and supports them to learn, whoever they are and whatever their abilities or requirements. This means making sure that teaching and the curriculum, school buildings, classrooms, play areas, transport and toilets are appropriate for all children at all levels. Inclusive education means all children learn together in the same schools. Inclusive education is an approach to schooling in which students with many different kinds of disabilities and learning needs are educated in classes with non-disabled and typically developing students. In an inclusive arrangement, students who need additional supports and services spend most of their time with their non-disabled peers rather than in separate classrooms or schools. This begins with a brief consideration of the ways inclusive education has been defined and an exploration of inclusion's roots in broader movements for civil rights in democratic societies. This is followed by a challenges of managing an inclusive classroom, along with several strategies that can help teachers address these challenges through the creation of a "culture of inclusion." Inclusive education as the means by which learners with learning barriers are educated in a mainstream school. The study was motivated by the belief that every learner must be given equal opportunity to be educated. This study has evaluated the perceptions of foundation level educators' on the implementation of inclusive education. The majority of educators lacked the necessary skills and resources that would ensure effective teaching and learning of learners with learning barriers. This deficiency is impacting negatively on the quality of teaching and learning. The experience and commitment of educators has allowed educators to use improvised methods to assist learners to cope in the mainstream classroom. Intervention strategies need to be implemented to accommodate second language learners within the mainstream classroom. This aspect poses a challenge to the educator as well as to other learners within the same classroom.

What is inclusive education?

Inclusive education is a child's right, not a privilege. Inclusion promotes quality and equitable education for all, without exclusion, including those who may be potentially marginalized by learning need or social position. An increasing awareness about the rights of children with disability to have access to the same educational services as children without a disability has led to the idea of inclusive education (UNESCO International Bureau of Education, 2009). Accordingly, the UNESCO (2005) stated that inclusive education is an approach that expresses how to change educational structures and other learning atmospheres to meet the needs of the variety of learners. Inclusion highlights opportunities for an equal involvement of individuals with disabilities (physical, social and emotional) when possible into typical education, but leaves accessible the probability of individual selections and possibilities for special aid and accommodations for persons who need it and want it (Rasmitadila & Tambunan, 2018). There is no universally accepted definition of inclusion and no consensus on standardized set of procedures that must be followed in order to practice it. One way to distinguish inclusion from another non-segregationist approach called mainstreaming is that in an inclusive classroom, there is a strong emphasis on trying to meet the diverse learning needs of all students without removing them from the classroom. By contrast, when children with special needs are mainstreamed, it usually means (at least in principle) that everyone in the class is expected to follow one standard curriculum regardless of their differences, or that particular children are taken out of the class for a large proportion of the day to receive their lessons and services. The term "inclusive education" is most often used to mean the inclusion of persons with physical and mental impairments, such as sensory or mobility limitations, intellectual disabilities, learning disabilities, language disorders, behavior disorders and autism spectrum disorders. Some educators and theorists also use "inclusion" in a broader sense, to refer to an educational system designed to ensure access for all groups that have been marginalized in society and in schools. Thus, inclusion is sometimes envisioned as the deliberate and self-conscious structuring of whole-school and classroom environments so that they are accessible and congenial not only to students with impairments, but also to those who can face exclusion or disempowerment due to their ethnicity, social class, gender, culture, religion, immigration history or other attributes. Because inclusion also has this broader meaning, it is sometimes endorsed as a means of achieving a more comprehensive form of social justice.

Inclusive Classroom: Challenges and Strategies

This can be especially daunting when the goal is a fully inclusive classroom. Students often have widely disparate capabilities, learning styles, ways of expressing themselves and modes of interacting with their physical and social environments. They can diverge significantly in their abilities to focus and pay attention, sit still, make sense of and respond to social cues, and regulate themselves in response to stimulation. Sometimes, a student's limitations and needs only become evident in the context of particular classroom activities and interactions. First, there is the challenge of how to create and maintain the order, structure, and safety that are necessary for a successful learning environment. Classrooms, like all other social situations, involve routinized activities and patterns of interaction. Teachers seek ways to include all their students in the social rituals through which learning and community building take place; they also strive to find creative, constructive ways to handle potential disruptions. Effective management thus is not only about accommodating students' learning needs, but also about helping them regulate their behavior. Second, there is the challenge of how to meet the learning, social and developmental needs of all students, both those who are typically developing and those with special needs and impairments. Here, the goal is to devise and implement academic and social curricula that can reach every child while also maximizing each individual's potential. Third, there is the challenge of how to confront the ever-present risk of stigmatizing those who are perceived as "different." In other words, there is a need to recognize and to try to lessen the many forms of literal and symbolic exclusion that may emerge, even in a setting that is devised to minimize these problems.

Encourage Extensive Research on Inclusive Education

Teachers are the main asset to deliver the content knowledge for the students, thereby promising career of the teacher should be declared by the ministry of education under inclusive education policy. It is necessary to provide understanding to parents who have normal children, about the goals in inclusive education. Positive parental perception would contribute to the success of programs that are related to inclusive education, which involve parents' role in giving understanding to their children on matters that are related to children with disabilities. The government should assist and encourage research institutes, universities, and NGOs to conduct extensive research that focuses on Inclusive Education, to identify the strengths, weaknesses, and challenges in implementing inclusive education from every specific factor that includes teachers, students, parents, education policy, and other important factors. Encourage researchers to investigate attitudes of teachers in teaching students in the classrooms. Behaviors may be affected by past experiences, prior knowledge and newly acquired. Attitudes play an important role in deciding behavior; thus, it is important to determine the factors that form the attitudes of traditional teachers when they seek to include disabled students. Teachers should be well prepared with module, supporting materials and proper infrastructure to help and guide the teacher to conduct the inclusive classroom.

Benefits of Inclusive Education

The benefits of Inclusive Education are numerous for both students with and without disabilities. Benefits of Inclusion for Students with Disabilities

- 1) Friendships
- 2) Increased social initiations, relationships and networks
- 3) Peer role models for academic, social and behavior skills
- 4) Increased achievement of IEP goals
- 5) Greater access to general curriculum
- 6) Enhanced skill acquisition and generalization
- 7) Increased inclusion in future environments
- 8) Greater opportunities for interactions
- 9) Higher expectations
- 10) Increased school staff collaboration
- 11) Increased parental participation
- 12) Families are more integrated into community

Benefits of Inclusion for Students without Disabilities

- 1) Meaningful friendships
- 2) Increased appreciation and acceptance of individual differences
- 3) Increased understanding and acceptance of diversity

- 4) Respect for all people
- 5) Prepares all students for adult life in an inclusive society
- 6) Opportunities to master activities by practicing and teaching others
- 7) Greater academic outcomes
- 8) All students' needs are better met, greater resources for everyone.

Building an Inclusive Education and Training System

Inclusive education has been the new reality in South Africa. Education is recognised as a fundamental right that must be available to all learners (South Africa, 1996 - Constitution, Act 108 of 1996). The Education White Paper 6 on Special Needs Education (South Africa 2001) reports the following about inclusive education:

- 1) Acknowledging that all children and youth can learn and that all children and youth need support;
- 2) Accepting and respecting that all learners are different in some way and have different learning needs which are equally valued and an ordinary part of our human experience;
- 3) Enabling education structures, systems and learning methodologies to meet the needs of all learners;
- 4) Acknowledging and respecting differences in learners whether due to age, gender, ethnicity, language, class, and disability or HIV status;
- 5) Changing attitudes, behaviour, teaching methodologies, curricula and the environment to meet the needs of all learners;
- 6) Maximising the participation of all learners in the culture and the curricula of educational institutions and uncovering and minimizing barriers to learning;
- 7) Empowering learners by developing their individual strengths and enabling them to participate critically in the process of learning; and
- 8) Acknowledging that learning also occurs in the home and community, and within formal and informal modes and structures.

Inclusive education addresses the educational needs of all learners in a non-threatening, supportive learning environment. This includes learners who were formally disadvantaged and excluded from education because of "barriers to learning" (Inclusive education 2009).

Operational Challenges and Problems of Inclusive Education

Prinsloo (2001) reports that there are many policies in respect of inclusive education and identifies the following problems:

- 1) Inclusive policies did not protect individual rights adequately;
- 2) The voices of the marginalised are often not heard;
- 3) The manner in which barriers to learning has been accommodated in the mainstream is unsatisfactory;
- 4) The community's contribution towards inclusive education is inadequate, especially in developing countries;
- 5) The implications of inclusive education on educators' roles have not been determined;
- 6) The manner in which special schools can promote inclusivity has not been utilised;
- 7) Classroom practice to respond to learner diversity needs support;
- 8) Identifying institutional environment that will contribute towards inclusivity;
- 9) Overcoming pressures to exclude inclusivity;
- 10) Identifying barriers that impede development of inclusiveness;
- 11) Addressing benefits to all learners in an inclusive classroom; and
- 12) Evaluating the effectiveness of inclusive education.

Recommendations

This section presents recommendations for the various concerns and issues for the effective implementation of inclusive education.

- 1) A substantial effort is required to implement the paradigm shift towards inclusive education and change the attitude of educators;
- 2) Educators need to be work shopped in greater intensity to prepare them to accommodate learners requiring support in the mainstream school. The support from the Department of Education should be on a continuous basis
- 3) The under-resourced schools and schools from impoverished backgrounds need learning material to

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accommodate the large numbers. These schools need to be supported financially by the Department of Education and the private sector;

- 4) Teacher education institutions need to embrace inclusive education more fully to produce graduates with the desired knowledge, attitudes and relevant skills;
- 5) Intervention for educators should include strategies to accommodate second language learners and teaching style; and
- 6) Parents from disadvantaged communities must be empowered and motivated to participate actively in the learners' learning programme.

Conclusion

The most effective way of ensuring advances in inclusive education is to adhere to the action plan that has been elaborated, and to take great care in allocating budget directly to the implementation of the specific activities. Direct support to teachers of students with special educational needs, as well as directly to those students, is crucial. Also, the Ministry itself must internally continue to educate itself on the importance of progressive inclusive education strategies to the overall quality of education. 'Inclusive and equitable quality education for all'. As it is apparent that countries around the world are making considerable efforts to apply the concept of No Child Left Behind in education by monitoring disparity and inequality and using the evidence to develop policies that promote equity and inclusion. Nevertheless, a common understanding of the concept of equity and, especially, inclusion is elusive. To conclude, the inclusion of students with disability in education context is not a one-man work. It needs a collaborative effort among the policy makers, middle management, and the teachers, not to mention the parents of the students should also disseminate the same concept of inclusion. As inclusive practices occupy a greater part of teachers' work in regular schools, a more comprehensive body of research is needed to monitor, inform, and improve current inclusive education efforts in the existing school system. Perhaps the greatest challenge would be the introduction of a comprehensive evaluation and feedback system that would continuously monitor the efficacy of the training programmes and respond appropriately and adequately to the emergent and unmet needs of all teachers. It would then be obvious that nothing short of a total system approach would suffice in confronting the problems of inclusive education.

References

- [1] Inclusive education. 2006. Equal opportunities for all learners to learn and succeed [online]. Available at <http://curriculum.pgwc.gov.za/site/40/view/96>[Assessed 19 May 2009].
- [2] Prinsloo, E. 2001. Working towards inclusive education in South African classrooms. *South African Journal of Education*, 21 (4): 344 – 348.
- [3] Rasmitadila, & SuryantiTambunan, A. R. (2018). Readiness of general elementary schools to become inclusive elementary schools: A preliminary study in Indonesia. *International Journal of Special Education*, 33(2), 366–381.
- [4] South Africa. 1996. Constitution, Act 108 of 1996. Pretoria: Government Printer.
- [5] South Africa. Department of Education. 2001. White Paper No 6. Special needs education. Pretoria: Government Printer.
- [6] UNESCO Bangkok. (2005). *Embracing Diversity: toolkit for creating inclusive, learning-friendly environments*. Bangkok: UNESCO.

STEM EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) has emerged as a global policy imperative of increasing significance. This paper examines the development of STEM Education as a primary focus for curriculum change, the various forms STEM Education takes in various nations, and the factors that influence international concern for STEM Education. The need to consider the STEM competencies that will prepare students for productive futures and the prospect of a vastly changing world of work that current students will enter is a key feature of concern for STEM in schools. A framework of STEM knowledge and skills derived from these concerns is presented in the paper. STEM is becoming more aligned with support for interdisciplinary approaches to education. The paper examines the implications for framing learning in the disciplinary subjects of mathematics and science in particular, arguing for the necessity of a productive alignment of disciplinary knowledge with interdisciplinary contexts. It also describes the various ways in which this is conceived of and pursued.

Keywords: *Education, Science, Technology, Mathematics Comparative Education, Teaching, Learning*

Introduction

STEM is an alternative educational strategy that focuses on connecting classroom learning to the actual world. The system works to increase the likelihood that everyone who goes through the educational system will play a significant role in society. This is due to its open-minded philosophy, which enables everyone to acquire the skills required for success in diverse fields of the labor market. STEAM is a STEM variant with added educational material (Science, Technology, Engineering, the Arts, and Mathematics). The addition of "Art" to STEAM expands the field of study to encompass humanities, dance, language, music, design, and visual art. For instance, a STEAM class might use drawings to assist students envision various concepts in order to give the concepts a deeper and more practical introduction.

Stem Education

There are academic requirements that dictate how classroom instruction is created and delivered to students, depending on the STEM subject area. Among these necessities are the following:

- 1) Problem-based education
- 2) Rigorous education supported by student involvement, instructor facilitation, and participation.
- 3) Personalized student support and individualized learning. This assistance could take the form of career planning, flexible instruction, and consulting.
- 4) Life skills, professional skills, collaboration, and technology utilization.

In order to feel a sense of community and belonging, students must treat one another with respect and trust, engage in extracurricular activities, and participate in school decision-making.

- 1) Gaining social and emotional skills.
- 2) Involvement in neighborhood activities.
- 3) Teachers exemplify what they preach by exhibiting a strong work ethic, pride in their institution, a commitment to professional growth, and an understanding of the leadership of the school in assisting staff members to advance their careers and transfer information.

STEM Education is crucial since there are a lot of new employments in sectors related to STEM, few high school graduates are proficient in these topics, and more kids in the United States are interested in pursuing STEM careers. To further promote equity and provide equal opportunity, efforts have been made to boost the proportion of minorities and women in STEM-related fields.

Innovation Skill

Skills for Innovation In today's world, where economic, technological, and industrial innovation and development are rapidly gaining importance, nations require educated, qualified individuals to expand and support

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their knowledge bases in this race. According to the OECD (2011), it is necessary to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for innovation at every level of K-12 education. Innovation skills provide qualifications and professional competence in the direction of objectives. When the research that has been done on innovation skills is looked at (Ananiadou & Claro, 2009; 2008 Kergroach; 2010 OECD, 2001 OECD; Stasz, 2001). Skills Essential to the Digital Age: Reading, writing, and arithmetic operations are all basic skills. The ability to use digital technology, communication tools, and networks is made possible by digital age literacy, which enables individuals to access and interpret information. According to the OECD (2008), digital literacy has grown to be as important as basic skills for future professions with the development of the Internet and information and communication technologies (ICT).

Academic Abilities

These are connected to subjects like geography, mathematics, and science. Typically, academic skills are acquired through education and applied in real life.

Technical Knowledge

These skills, which include academic knowledge and abilities, are necessary for professional life. In response to complex issues in industrial development and national policies, this skill is becoming increasingly important for competence in product, service, and development processes.

Common Skills

This skill set includes critical thinking, problem-solving, and creative thinking, understanding, and handling difficult circumstances.

Social Abilities

Motivation, communication, collaboration, and responsibility skills are all examples of social skills that enable individuals to interact with other groups or within a group. The development of comprehension, openness, and awareness skills for intercultural communication, as well as the capacity to read and control ones owns behaviors as well as that of others are crucial. Leadership: Team management, leadership, and coordination abilities are all part of this skill.

People who are successful in the innovation process are required to have these described skills. The following is how Green, Jones, and Miles (2007) define effective skills and innovation processes: They are:

- 1) **Selection of resources and concepts:** The gathering of resources, the selection of appropriate resources, and the identification of ideas are all included in this initial stage. There is a review of the sources, an interpretation of new information, an assessment of their validity, and a discussion of ideas. Fundamental, scholarly, general, furthermore, specialized abilities are significant at this stage.
- 2) **Idea generation for new innovations:** Individuals or diverse groups come together at this stage to effectively collaborate, make decisions, and share ideas. At this point, social and leadership skills become more important.
- 3) **Testing and distribution:** The trade, benefits, and risks are evaluated at this point. The product of choice ought to be based on the requirements and preferences of the customer. Engineering and marketing expertise are necessary for product development and commercialization at this stage. Innovation tracking, risk management, and identification are required.
- 4) **Expansion and implementation:** Project management, technology transfer, and supply chain coordination are all included at this point.

Communication and Collaboration

Students interact in a communicative and collaborative manner in STEM education when engineering design-focused work is involved (Crismond & Adams, 2012). In engineering programs for grades K-12, communication and teamwork have become increasingly important (ABET, 2012). Students in STEM education present their design projects in teams as engineers (Borrego, Karlin, McNair, & Beddoes, 2013). Students in STEM education communicate through written, verbal, visual, and technological means. Students can effectively communicate their ideas through fluent speech, correct reading and writing, and the use of digital technologies.

The following is an illustration of the significance of clear communication: Trilling and Fadel (2009).

- 1) People who can communicate effectively;

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- 2) In a variety of settings, verbal, written, and other forms of communication, they can express their thoughts and ideas.
- 3) Are good listeners who help people make sense of knowledge, value, and attitude?
- 4) Capable of communicating for a variety of purposes (informing, motivating, persuading, etc.)
- 5) Capability to work together toward a common objective and to be adaptable and flexible when making decisions together
- 6) Individual participation in group work and shared accountability.

According to Trilling & Fadel (2009), students' social skills are developed through physical or virtual environments of communication and collaboration with others. The OECD (2011) says that social skills like communication and collaboration are important for working together in a globalized world and helping each other out. The individual's professional and career work is affected by their capacity to work in multicultural groups.

Conclusion

The assumption that the development of a populace with STEM skills is an important key to this and the concern of nation states to build strong economies and improve societal wellbeing are both reflected in the global focus on STEM education. Calls for a shift in the focus of STEM curricula in schools have arisen as a result of perceptions that today's youth are less interested in STEM subjects and predictions that the future of work will place an increasing emphasis on STEM-related transferable skills like critical thinking, creative problem solving, design thinking, and collaborative teamwork. These calls amount to an argument that school mathematics and science content and pedagogy do not engage students in the kinds of knowledge and skills that will best prepare them for the future. Therefore, the STEM phenomenon poses a threat to "business as usual" in school science and mathematics. This is true for all levels of education because early decisions about whether or not to participate in STEM careers can be made. Interdisciplinary approaches to mathematics and science education, based on real-world problem-solving and cross-subject interactions, are increasingly being promoted in STEM rhetoric. STEAM, where the letter "A" stands for creative art and design, has been pursued as a strategy to boost creativity in STEM education practices in a number of nations. STEM advocacy has rekindled a long-standing interest in interdisciplinary approaches for mathematics. Interdisciplinary mathematics faces both opportunities and challenges, according to this review. To begin, there is a dearth of research that could elucidate the most effective strategies and potential outcomes. In the initiatives that have been investigated, the nature of integration varies greatly, as do the research methods used and the outcomes that have been emphasized.

References

- [1] Barnes, M. (2000). "'Magical' moments in mathematics: Insights into the process of Coming to know." *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 20(1), 33-43.
- [2] Barrett, J. E., & Clements, D. H. (2003). Quantifying path length: Fourth-grade Children are developing abstractions for linear measurement. *Cognition and Instruction*, 21(4), 475-520.
- [3] Beauchamp, M., & Beauchamp, C. (2012). Understanding the neuroscience and Education connection: themes emerging from a review of the literature. *Neuroscience in education: the good, the bad, and the ugly*, 13-30.
- [4] Becker, K., & Park, K. (2011). Effects of integrative approaches among science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) subjects on students' learning: A preliminary meta-analysis. *Journal of STEM Education: Innovations & Research*, 12.
- [5] Berlin, D. F., & Lee, H. (2003). A bibliography of integrated science and mathematics Teaching and learning literature, Vol. 2: 1991–2001. *School Science and Mathematics Association Topics for Teachers Series Number 7*. Columbus, OH: ERIC Clearinghouse for Science, Mathematics, and Environmental Education.
- [6] Berlin, D. F., & Lee, H. (2005). Integrating science and mathematics education: Historical analysis. *School Science and Mathematics*, 105(1), 15-24.
- [7] Binkley, M., Erstad, O., Herman, J., Raizen, S., Ripley, M., Miller-Ricci, M., & Rumble, M. (2012). Defining twenty-first century skills. In *Assessment and Teaching of 21st century skills* (pp. 17-66). Springer, Dordrech

INFLUENCE OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON SELECTED PHYSIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOMOTOR VARIABLES ON SPECIAL CHILDREN

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Abstract

In the present study, the investigator has been enthusiastic to know the changes brought about by yogic practices on selected physiological and psychological variables. To facilitate the study, 30 students from the Sahrudaya disability management ,hanamkonda and Shri Anthoyodaya Special education center, Warangal-20, were randomly selected and divided into two groups. Out of the two groups, one served as control and the other served as experimental group. The yoga training programme was given to the experimental group on six days a week for a duration of one and a half hour every day for a period of 6 weeks. During this period, the control group was not given any training. The data were collected on the selected physiological and psychomotor variables namely vital capacity and hand-eye co-ordination immediately after 6 weeks yoga training programme. The significance of the difference between the experimental and control group was found out through the analysis of co-variance. Vital capacity and hand-eye coordination (right & left hand) were significantly improved through yoga training programme.

Introduction

Yoga is a discipline which seeks to bring the internal environment of an individual under his control, thereby assisting a happy adjustment of the individual within himself as well as with his surroundings. Yoga is concerned with techniques for bodily health, techniques of silencing the breath, behavioral discipline and mental concentration. An individual who masters these four aspects of yoga is said to be a perfect individual. Yoga may, thus, be described as the science of personality. It acts as an effective cleanser in life. Maximum benefit by minimum expenditure of energy is the result of yogic practice. Patanjali's Yoga has essentially to do with the mind and its modifications. It deals with the training of the mind to achieve oneness with the Universe. Incidental to this objective are the acquisition of siddhis or powers. The aim of Patanjali Yoga is to set man free from the cage of matter. Mind is the highest form of matter and man free from this dragnet of Chitta or Ahankara (mind or ego) becomes a pure being.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the effects of yogic practices on selected physiological and psychomotor variables of college women

Hypotheses

1 It was hypothesized that the yogic training may have positive effects on the selected physiological variable of college women. It was also hypothesized that the yogic training may have positive effects on the selected psychomotor variable of college women.

To achieve the purpose of the present study, the yogic practices such as Padmasana, Padahasthasana, Sarvangasana, Matsyasana, Halasana, Trikonasana, Anuloma-viloma pranayama, Kapalabhati, Bastrika pranayama, Trataka, Meditation, and Savasana were given to the experimental group. In the present study, the investigator has been enthusiastic to know the changes brought about by yogic practices on selected physiological and psychological variables. To facilitate the study, thirty students from the Sahrudaya disability management ,hanamkonda and Shri Anthoyodaya Special education center, Warangal, -20, were randomly selected and divided into two groups. Out of the two groups, one served as control and the other served as experimental group. The yoga training programme was given to the experimental group on six days a week for the duration of one and a half hour every day for a period of six weeks. During this period, the control group was not given any training. The data were collected on the selected physiological and psychomotor variables namely vital capacity and hand-eye coordination immediately after six weeks of the yoga training programme. The significance of the difference between the experimental and control group was found out through the analysis of co-variance. The F-ratio for the adjusted means was computed through the analysis of covariance. The level of confidence was set at 0.05 level.

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Table 1: Computation of Analysis of Co-Variance of Adjusted Post Test on Vitas Capacity of Experimental and Control Group

Mean	Experimental group(N=15)	Control Group (N=15)	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-ratio
Post test mean	2007.85	1538.82	B: W:	161569.27 236632.00	1 27	161569.27 8764.15	184.35*
B-Between group *- Significant at 0.05 level W-Within group							

The adjusted post-test mean values on vital capacity of experimental and control groups were 2007.85 and 1538.82. The obtained F-ratio of 184.35 for adjusted post-test means is greater than the required value of 4.21 for degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table 2: Computation of Analysis of Co-Variance of Adjusted Post-Test on Hand-Eye Coordination (Right Hand) of Experimental and Control Group

Mean	Experimental group(N=15)	Control Group (N=15)	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-ratio
Post test mean	65.79	131.47	B: W:	31912.06 39417	1 27	31912.06 1459.89	21.86*
B-Between group* -Significant at 0.05 level W-Within group							

The adjusted post-test mean values on hand-eye coordination (right hand) of experimental and control groups were 65.79 and 131.47. The obtained F-ratio of 21.86 for adjusted post-test means is greater than the required table value of 4.21 for degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table 3: Computation of Analysis of Co-Variance of Adjusted Post-Test on Hand-Eye Coordination (Left Hand) of Experimental and Control Group

Mean	Experimental group(N=15)	Control Group (N=15)	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-ratio
Post test mean	71.32	153.08	B: W:	48775.14 44927.45	1 27	48775.14 1663.98	29.31
B-Between group*-Significant at 0.05 level W-Within group.							

The adjusted post-test mean values on hand-eye coordination (left hand) of experimental and control groups were 71.32 and 153.08. The obtained F-ratio of 29.31 for adjusted post-test means is greater than the required table value of 4.21 for degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Conclusion

Vital capacity was significantly improved through yoga training programme. Hand-eye coordination (right hand) was significantly improved through yoga training programme. Hand-eye coordination (left hand) was significantly improved through yoga training programme.

References

- [1] Chanavirat et al. Yeus exercise increases chest wall expansion and lung volumes in young healthy thias. Journal of physiological sciences 2006. 19(1), pp. 1-7 .
- [2] The Sahasi, G. A 27, 33-35 replicated study on the effects of yoga on cognitive functions. Indian psychological review: 1984.27,33-35.
- [3] Sandy Kimbrother of Effect of inverted you position in short term memory. The online Journal of sports choling 2005.
- [4] Sohi, Rachina. Effect of sadishodhan pranayamin on forced vital capacity Yoga department, Dev Sanskrit University Shantikun, Haridwar 2001.

INFLUENCE OF YOGIC PRACTICES AMONG INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ASTHAMATIC MEN

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Abstract

The purpose of life is to trade happy life. Health is the very foundation of happy life. Health status in India is alarming and apprehensive. Every 10 seconds one person is affected by Asthma. It affects people of all ages, but it most often starts in childhood. Among children more boys have asthma than girls. But among adults, more women have disease than men. Yogic practices restore the depleted and blocked pranic energy channels. The first necessary step is to remove constipation. Yogic practices increase the elasticity of lungs, ribs, muscles and diaphragm; stabilize the nervous system to soothe airways. The purpose of the study was to find out the influence of yogic practices among Asthmatic men. Allergy, stress, faulty genes inheritance, house dust, cat, dog, danger (hair) smoking artificial coloring drugs, cold, air, water places irritant fumes air pollution excess secretion of hormones, change of weather obesity, it was concluded that influence of yogic practice secures information technology Asthmatic men. Yoga techniques are beneficial as an aid to the management of asthma.

Keywords: *Yoga Practices, Asthma, Information Technology.*

Introduction

Asthma is primarily a disease of the respiratory system. Asthma is a chronic (long term) lung disease. It inflames and narrows the airways. The airways are the tubes that carry air in and out of lungs. Inflamed airways make the airways swollen and very sensitive. They tend to react strongly to certain substances that are breathed in. When the airways react, the muscles around them tighten. This causes airways to narrow and less air flows to the lungs. The swelling also can worsen making the airways even narrower. Cells in the airways may make more mucus than normal. There is a wheezing cough and a sense of suffocation. It may last for only a few minutes, or may continue for hours or even days, leaving the patient in a stage of exhaustion. It affects people of all ages, but it most often starts in childhood. Among children, more boys have asthma than girls. But among adults, more women have the disease than men. The prevalence of asthma worldwide is around 300 million and in India more than 20 million. In the last ten years, the prevalence of asthma has increased by more than 50%. India is the ninth most polluted nation in the world. Only 12% of city dwellers breathe safe air in India, 18% of children in Bangalore have Asthma. Yoga practices increase the elasticity of lungs, ribs, muscles and diaphragm, stabilize the nervous system to soothe airways, provide ventilation to every cell which promotes longevity, prevents toxins and infections, avoid cell wastage, increase oxygen uptake by providing fresh blood, excrete sputter easily, allow white blood cells to circulate well.

Objective of the Study

Regular yogic practice restores the depleted and blocked pranic energy channels. The first necessary step is to remove constipation. Yogic practices increase the elasticity of lungs, ribs, muscles and diaphragm, stabilize the nervous system to soothe airways.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to find out the influence of yogic practices among Information Technology Asthmatic men.

Review of the Related Literature

Demeke Mekonnen and Andale Mossie (2019) studied the effect of yoga on patterns of clinical features, peak expiratory flow rates and use of drugs in asthmatic patients. A preliminary controlled clinical trial study was conducted on 24 volunteer asthmatic patients who were getting support at the missionary of charity. They were grouped in yoga and control groups. An Indian yoga expert through a translator conducted the training on yogic practice, yogic posture, breath slowing technique and discussion at the end. Then, the yoga groups were supervised for four weeks taking yoga exercise daily for 50 minutes. Peak expiratory flow rate was taken using the mini Wright peak flow meter and vital signs were measured in both groups. Data were analysed using web-based Graph pad quick calcs statistical software. The male to female ratio was 1:1 in both cases and control groups (81.66.7%) were Christian and 9 (75.0%) were farmers. The yoga group showed 66.7% reduction in the use of salbutamol puff

and 58.3% salbutamol tablets There was a 10% increment in the PEFr in the yoga group while only 2% in the control group. There was statistically significant reduction in day and night asthma attacks in the yoga group. Yoga Exercise among asthmatic patients resulted in a decreased number of day and night attacks and use of drugs. It also shows significant improvement in the peak expiratory flow rate. Further large scale study is recommended.

Methodology

Asthma is a respiratory disease involving the airways or the bronchial tubes. The airways are swollen in an asthma patient, and get inflamed further when triggered by symptoms, narrowing them and making it difficult for the person to breathe. The problem significantly increased from the 1960s and now accounts for 397,100 deaths globally. Yoga helps to breathe better Although breathing is a natural process, with yoga, it is possible to change the breathing pattern and habits for a more holistic breathing experience that will help to tackle asthma problem effectively. Along with it, yoga has other physical and mental benefits. all working together in tandem to help to combat the asthma menace.

Causes

Allergy, stress, faulty genes inheritance, house dust, cat dog danger their , smoking, artificial coloring, drugs, cold air, water places, instant fumes, air pollution, excess secretion of hormones histamine Leukotrienes, change of weather, obesity, acidity, negative thoughts, depression,spiced food, excessive travel excessive sex, excessive fasting, tobacco, constipation, acid reflex lack of exercise, molds, pollen grains, industrial smoke, diesel fumes, dietary indiscretion.

Signs and Symptoms

Chest tightness, shortness of breath, sweating, acidity, coughing, breathing difficulties tiredness wheezing, sneezing running nose, constipation, chest pain, rapid heart rate, weak pulse rate, pain in abdomen, pain in breathing, lethargy, nasal congestion, sore throat, bead ach trouble in sleeping.

Remedy

Yoga, walking, fasting once in a month, Hydropathic baths, cold bath in hot times hot hath in cold times, inhaler, swimming, running jogging, use warm clothes, steroids, stay away from smokers, incense sticks, sunbath, hot foot bath, foot & arm bath, steam bath hot and cold fermentation, chest pack, steam inhalation, sun bath, acupuncture, acupressure.

Avoid

Over eating, citrus fruits, red pumpkin, fried items, white sugar, cold drinks, bananas groundnut, dairy products cabbage, red meat bread, cakes, ghee, oily foods, rice, sweets, cold areas, processed fried, white flour, packed juices, milk, milk products, sour fruits, curd, worry, constipation.

Yogic Practices

Loosening the joints, Suryanamaskar, Viksasani, Trikonasana, Padahastasana, Moordhasana, Sarvangasana, Matsyasana, Bhujangasana, shalabasana, Dhanurasana, Ushtrasana, Shasangasana, Adhamukha Svanasana, Ardha Matsyendrasana, Paschimottanasana, Gomukhasana. Savasana, Ujjayi Pranayama, Kapaibhati in Padmasana, Bhastrika pranayama in vajrasana, Nadi Shodhana pranayama in Siddhasana.

Conclusion

It was concluded that influence of yogic practices cures Information Technology Asthmatic men Yoga techniques are beneficial as an aid to the management of asthma.

Reference

- [1] Demeke Mekonnen and Andualem Mossie (2010). Clinical Effects of Yoga on Asthmatic Patients
- [2] A Preliminary Clinical Trial Ethiop J Health Sci, 2012)-107-112
- [3] <http://www.ingentaconnect.com>
- [4] Elangovan R (2016), Fundamentals of Yoga, (1st ed), Chennai, India: Ashwin Publications, PP 7-23

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PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUES TO SUPPORT STUDENTS' HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

The goal of educators is to meet the academic criteria and to educate the students on the proper techniques for dealing with life's obstacles. They make an effort to involve the learner on all levels, including the intellect, spirit, and body. The purpose of the study is to identify educational approaches and the advantages of holistic education for students and to study about the pedagogical techniques used by the teacher in the classroom to enhance students' overall development. The National Education Policy 2020 strives to provide a holistic and multidisciplinary approach to education, enhancing the educational sector and making it more productive and inclusive. Therefore, teachers can help students receive a holistic education in the classroom by encouraging problem-solving, expanding learning opportunities, creating integrated programs, strengthening relationships between teacher and student, boosting self-confidence, and supporting emotional and mental behavior.

Key words: *Holistic Education, Pedagogical Techniques, National educational Policy, Multidisciplinary*

Introduction

Holistic Education is an educational concept that emphasizes the value of creating homeostasis and is founded on the idea that each person derives identity, meaning, and purpose from their ties to the natural world. A teaching strategy known as holistic education places equal emphasis on students' social and academic demands. The goal of educators is to meet the academic criteria. educate the pupils on the proper techniques for dealing with life's obstacles. They make an effort to involve the learner on all levels, including the intellect, spirit, and body. The focus of this instructional strategy is on creating a supportive environment in schools. Along with the pupils' excellent social behaviors and cognitive abilities. Holistic learning is transformative learning that emphasizes striking a balance between managing the proportion of the inner educational substance process and developing the inner capability of the learners. Currently, there are numerous ways that holistic education management or education for overall development has been developed.

Objective of the Study

- 1) The purpose of the study is to identify educational approaches and the advantages of holistic education for students.
- 2) To study about the pedagogical techniques used by the teacher in the classroom to enhance students' overall development.

Holistic Education NEP 2020

The comprehensive National Education Policy 2020 strives to provide a holistic and multidisciplinary approach to education, enhancing the educational sector and making it more productive and inclusive. Education that is holistic and transdisciplinary is highly valued by NEP 2020. "Pedagogy must adapt to make education more immersive, comprehensive, integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented, learner-centered, discussion-based, flexible, and, of course, pleasurable," the statement states. Ancient Indian literature and rituals have traces of such an educational system. Vedic students had to take math, science, and geometry classes as well as lectures on morality, ethics, soft skills, and value education to build both their professional and vocational talents. The inclusion of Multidisciplinary Education in the NEP 2020 is a good improvement and make the students in productive and inclusive manner.

The Components of Holistic Education to Build Competencies

According to Forbes (2004), Freedom is a complicated psychological idea of autonomy, or as it is frequently referred to "inner emancipation." Good judgment - directly tied to autonomy and self-governance. Meta-learning - which emphasizes how each learner learns. Social ability -The ability to be "in society, but not of it" through gaining more than just social skills. Ideals refinement: This refers to the pupils' personal growth, not the ethos or values of the institution. Self-knowledge is a broad notion that includes understanding one's nature and going beyond only learning about oneself.

Holistic Educational Approaches

Developing a child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual qualities is the aim of holistic education. While a single overall principle informs holistic education, teachers may use a variety of techniques to foster a culture of holistic learning. **Experiential Learning:** Experiential learning centers offer practical educational opportunities. Problem-solving activities are frequently used in holistic, experiential strategies to solve societal issues or develop new goods. **Self-Guided Learning:** In self-guided learning environments, teachers give students the freedom to study in the way that best suits them and at their own pace. **Community Schools:** Teachers collaborate with community members to offer integrated support and increased learning opportunities, such as after-school and summer programs. **Interdisciplinary Coursework:** The notion that pupils' cognitive development is enhanced when several courses are addressed together is one component of holistic education.

Advantages of Holistic Education

Holistic education has several advantages. It enables students to identify and pursue their passions. It fosters respect for all parts of life, including the academic, athletic, social, etc. Students gain knowledge on how to get along with others and look after them. They learn the abilities needed to overcome obstacles. Students will have a sense of responsibility, be self-assured, and be socially aware. Students learn to respect one another's diversity, and it aids in the development of strong critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Pedagogical Techniques to Support Students' Holistic Education

Hands-on Learning: Schools that emphasize experiential learning offer students hands-on learning opportunities. To decide which learning styles are most successful for them, students investigate several learning styles in small groups. **Self-guided learning:** Teachers let students pick the learning methods and pace that work best for them. Personalization is possible in the self-guided culture, which helps to compensate for one learning model's shortcomings. **Schools as communities:** Schools are built on the premise that connections with one's surroundings help one find meaning in life. Teachers collaborate with community people to offer integrated support and increased learning opportunities, including families, citizens, organizations, and officials. **Interdisciplinary education:** When several subjects are covered at once, cognitive development is boosted. Some schools are developing integrated programs where instructors from many fields collaborate to deliver courses that are topical and examine problems from a variety of angles.

Conclusion

Therefore, teachers can help students receive a holistic education in the classroom by encouraging problem-solving, expanding learning opportunities, creating integrated programs, strengthening relationships between teacher and student, boosting self-confidence, and supporting emotional and mental behavior. Teachers should encourage students to consistently improve their skills. The teachers must be able to assist and counsel the students. A comprehensive curriculum provides a friendly learning environment and takes into account various learning preferences. It is more likely that students will graduate from school with a sense of civic responsibility, self-assurance, and self-awareness.

References

- [1] Shukla, B., Joshi, M., Sujatha, R., Beena, T., & Kumar, H. (2022). Demystifying Approaches of Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education for Diverse Career Opportunities: NEP 2020. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 15(14), 603–607. <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/v15i14.2296>
- [2] Sukhonthachit .P., &Rattanawicha.S. (2022). Holistic Learning In Technology Age. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(8), 6668-6678. <http://journalppw.com>
- [3] <https://soeonline.american.edu/blog/what-is-holistic-education/>
- [4] <https://www.oakridge.in/blogs/how-to-promote-holistic-development-in-children/>
- [5] <https://ezyschooling.com/parenting/expert/Holistic-development-and-its-benefits>
- [6] <https://www.oakridge.in/blogs/how-to-promote-holistic-development-in-children/>

PERCEPTION ON EMPLOYABILITY SKILL THROUGH COMMUNICATION COMPETENCY

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Abstract

Employability does not simply mean good technical understanding and subject knowledge for finding a job. It is about relating personal development and other associated skills that influence individuals' ability to find, obtain and be successful in their selected employment. An extensive definition of employability that supports this goal is, "the set of achievements, understandings and personal attributes that support a person in managing their careers". Employability can be enriched if the knowledge is obtained for the personal development by being aware of the capabilities, one can make the most of their chance at work and career plans. There is a growing need to enhance the communication competency to enhance the employability. The paper attempts to highlight communication competency as an essential factors to know the how it contribute to a wider range of outcomes, such as increased confidence and recognition of personal achievement, that enhance the claims in a competitive world but also ongoing development as individuals and lifelong learners. In today's competitive world, a communication competency is the most sought after quality of an educated person. Communication is a wide activity involving words, body language, voice tone and volume, the topic under discussion, the prejudgments that people bring to the topic. Communication is efficient when the recipient of a message understands its meaning and can indicate that meaning back to the speaker or sender of the message. Unsuccessful communication occurs when the meaning is not understood.

Keywords: *Employability, Communication Skills, Personal Attributes, Communication Competency*

Introduction

In today's competitive world, a communication skill is the most sought after quality of an educated person. Communication is an intricate activity involving words, body language, voice tone and volume, the theme under discussion, the prejudgments that people bring to the theme. Communication is successful when the recipient of information recognizes its meaning and can express that meaning back to the speaker or sender of the information. Unsuccessful communication occurs when the information is not recognized. Good communication competency not only gives an edge in getting the desired employment but also help to be more efficient in the job. Communication competency is one of the basic traits of management. It deliver as a foundation for planning as it assist in performing jobs and responsibilities effectively, organizing and controlling is not possible without written and oral communication to achieve the task. The most important effects that good communication can confer upon an organization is fundamentally the fact that there will be clearly in terms of what is expected and what is approved as part of the mission of the organization and as part of their common vision of a aim. To achieve development in career one must know how to utilize one or several modes of communication to get their ideas across, to advance their missions, to engage others, and to enlist people support to be effectual in their work and personal connection.

Employability

Employability Skills can be defined as the transmittable skills needed by a special person to make them 'employable'. Along with ethical technical understanding and subject knowledge, employers often outline a set of skills that they want from an employee. These skills are what they believe will provide the employee to carry out their part to the most of their capacity. Employability counts on the knowledge, skills and attitudes, how you utilize those benefits, and how you give them to employers. Employability skills are the basic skills and traits needed in nearly all job. These are the general skills that make someone advisable to an organization. Hiring managers almost always look for candidates with these skills. Employability skills are occasionally called foundational skills or job-readiness skills. Employability skills include the soft skills that permit you to work good with others, appeal knowledge to resolve problems, and to fit into any work situation.

Communication competence is how clearly a person can communicate their thoughts and ideas to others. You may find it favorable to enhance competency when you're communicating to help you achieve your aim in a

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discussion, such as persuading an audience. Understanding what communication competence is can help you enhance the way of speaking with others efficiently. Understanding the types of communication skills and competencies is an important skill both for managers and business owners as well as employees.

Verbal Communication Skills

Verbal communication skills are very significant and must be sharpened, especially in a job in which employees deal with the public. Good communication requires straight forward language that is neither too flowery or too clearly. It is necessary to be able to use the spoken word to get your point across simply. Higher levels of communication competencies give out with compelling speaking and these skills are essential for management level employees and those in marketing positions within a company. All employees can benefit from public speaking courses, which help enhance these key communication skills.

Nonverbal Communication Skills

Nonverbal communication is much more challenging for several people. It includes body language and the cues that are given off while listening to someone else speak. Those in customer service positions want to have a highly enhanced competency level in listening. Nodding of the head, inclining towards the speaker and displaying an open body let a speaker know that you are listening and hearing what they have to say.

Written Communication Skills

One of the overlooked areas of communication is the written word. Even the most basic position in a company needs employees to have effective written communication skills. Proper spelling, grammar usage and a professional way of imparting ideas are significant competencies that must be mastered. Written communication that is badly worded, misspelled or full of errors detracts from the overall information that is being imparted. This is even more important when dealing with the public through written communication. People judge others by the way they write and it is vital to make sure that written communication is professional.

Communication Styles and Competencies

Within these three important types of communication lies a subset of ways and individual competencies. Individual may be very skilled at verbal communication, but absent in written communication skills. Time must be taken to enhance all three skills equally. The style of communication is also very significant. Some communicators are upbeat and impressive, while others are more quiet and subdued. The style of communication should match the tone of the message that is being delivered.

Communication is Imperative in Enhancing the Employability

Communication plays the most important role in the employability enhancement process. Employers are looking for workers who can represent themselves professionally through verbal and non-verbal communication. The capability to interact successfully and change the style appropriately is significant all through the working relations. Individuals become successful in establishing efficient communication when people can understand what they are talking about or listen to and assimilate their points. They can interact with others through simple and clear terms. Communication not only indicates the good use of verbal speeches but also includes building kinships between sender and receiver through non-verbal activities or body language. However, a deeper understanding of communication competency helps in good comprehension of facts that can optimize the employability.

Helps in Structuring Goals

Communication indicates being clear and good about what we want to achieve. It is the influential power of any individual through which he can generate interest among employers.

Promotes Motivation

Communication plays an important role in assisting motivation among employees. For example, a person with well-spoken power is more confident than a person who lacks to explain his abilities.

Helps in Making Important Decisions

Communication is considered as the source of message that helps any individual or group to make good

decisions regarding tasks or aim. For insistence, the decision-making team will rely on the employees who can detail on the facts and figures more confidently and effectively.

Strengthens Employees' Performances

Communication helps in several administrative processes and assists in controlling employees' behavior effectively. For example, good communication strengthens the policies of the organizations and employees' activities that ultimately control the management functions.

Enhances the Ability of Effective Interactions

Communication enhances the socialization, a significant aspect of employability development. For example, a person with better communication skills can easily socialize with his/her fellow employees that enhance the possibilities of getting a better understanding of the job activities and opportunities.

Conclusion

Employability skills allow the learner to withstand the high levels of competition at every phase of life. Language, being the source of language proficiency, facilitates and enhances other required skills like soft skills, presentation skills, and, above all, communication skills. In the management and human resource sector, communication competency skills are considered as the key eligibility criteria for selecting any employee. People believe that the enhancement of communication competency is only possible by developing their spoken skills. However, this phenomenon is partially correct because there are many other traits also associated with the communication. Active listening is one of the most important parts of it. We can be an effective speaker only when we can be a good listener. Therefore, under the light of employability enrichment, it is necessary to strengthen communication in a way to develop aspirants for their good professional future.

Reference

- [1] Ahmad, K. (2012). Relationship between employability and graduates' skill. *International Business Management*, 6, 440-445.
- [2] Benerjee, A. K. (2002). *New directions in grammar and English language teaching*. Jaipur, India: Pointer Publications.
- [3] Bharathi, A. V. (2013). *Identification of problems in teaching-learning English in commerce colleges of the Kachchh District* (Unpublished thesis). Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda.
- [4] Chithra, R. (2013). *Employability skills: A study on the perception of the engineering students and their prospective employers*. *Global Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 3(5), 525-534.
- [5] Dutta, A. K. (2015). *The significance of English language as a tool for employable skills*. In *English language teaching in India: Problems and prospects*. Guwahati, India: Olympia Prakashan.
- [6] Dutta, P. K. (2005, November 28). *Higher education in 21st century: Challenges and opportunities*. *University News (An AIU Newsletter)*, 43, 1-9.
- [7] ET Bureau. (2011, April 7). *Only 28% IT graduates readily employable: Nasscom*. *The Economic Times*. Retrieved from <http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com>
- [8] Fernandez, A. M. (2006, September 4). *Curriculum redesign in the era of knowledge economy*. *University News (An AIU Newsletter)*, 44, 79-80.
- [9] Haseen, T. (2005). *Current challenges in education*. Hyderabad, India: Neelkamal Publications.

IMPRESSION OF ATTITUDE AND COMPETENCY TOWARDS ICT ON JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Computers can be used independently, in small or large groups or by the teacher with the entire class. Every approach has been revealed to be effective, though there are some modifications in approaches and as a result upon conclusions. The alteration comes in the way in which the teacher practices the different prospects to help learners talk and think almost their work. Those perform better than groups when resonant out drill and exercise procedures. This may be for they complete more on their specific or as it is challenging to set responsibilities with an appropriate level of experiment for more than one learner. However, there is also evidence that computers can be used effectively to support pupils' talk and improve their discussion when they work in small groups on collaborative tasks and even 'directive' software can support discussion and reasoning. This study perceived the attitude, competency, job satisfaction of secondary school teachers toward using ICT tools in education. Teachers may need to teach pupils how to interact with each other when using the computer collaboratively so that effective learning can take place. While ICT is used to promote conversation in small groups and in entire class settings this can help to develop pupils' thinking and understanding across the curriculum in a selection of subjects and with a choice of effects.

Keywords: *ICT, Attitude, Teaching Learning Process, Competency, Job Satisfaction*

Introduction

Information and communication technology, or ICT, is definite as the combination of informatics technology with other, interrelated technologies, precisely communication technology. The ICT technology also manifests two key assumptions about how computers can assist learning. First, the users' ability to interact with ICT is intently defined in ways designed specifically to promote learning with the tools. Second, computers are viewed as a medium for teaching and learning. ICT also help teachers in the following ways:

- 1) ICT enables to enhance the initial preparation by giving good teaching materials to use.
- 2) With the help of ICT, teachers can access to colleagues, institutions, universities, centre of expertise, rich resources and cyber space and national organization like UGC, NCTE, NCERT, NAAC etc,
- 3) ICT enable to interact with students over a physical distance,
- 4) ICT enable to access online libraries, journals and research to enable individual learning.
- 5) ICT enable to give feedback of student's performance and evaluating students, work objectively and fast without biases.
- 6) ICT provide lifelong and professionally developed courses at virtual situation, training on demand, orientation, and refresher course through video conferencing or on-line.

Several altered types of technology can be used to support and enhance teaching. The whole thing from video content and digital moviemaking to laptop computing and handheld knowledge has been used in classrooms. Likewise, new uses of technology for instance pod casting are constantly emerging (Marshall, 2002). To Marshall, different technologies provide different kinds of content and serve different resolutions in the classroom.

Teacher's Attitude Towards ICT

Attitudes are in turn influenced by and influence these institutions. By knowing about the attitude of a person come to know that what in one's life is significant or insignificant. So the importance of attitude in life is universally acknowledged. Attitudes determine one's actions. They powerfully determine our behavior towards profession and also towards other areas of life. Attitude supply the code by which the behavior of the individual and others is judged, Furthermore, attitudes supply principles based on which choices are made. It also determines attractions and repulsions for the most of the objects in one's life. Since the goal of education system is wholesome development of human personality. It is essentially concerned itself with the creation of an environment in which the development of all-round personality can be facilitated and ensured. Hence there is a close connection between education and attitudes. The quality of human resources is a major factor of success for all the countries in the new century. In this global village, the quality of the intellectual capital of a country is

becoming more important than the financial natural or other sources. To survive in this highly competitive world the first requirement is its trained technical people. The strength of all countries lies in their abilities to produce, absorb, and disseminate knowledge. That's why the system particularly the education system• needs to prepare such manpower which can face the challenges of in this changing scenario where technology rules our life. So the introduction and development of ICT to schools depends only on quality and ability of teachers. As is often said, "An educational system can only be as good as its teachers". Today in cybernetic society of c-education, c-business, c-tutoring teachers are not only knowledge givers but also harbingers for the changes in soda-economic systems. The teachers and educationists who are still unfamiliar with computers may easily feel the threat of professional obsolescence.

Teachers Competency towards ICT

Teachers competency influence students, learning achievement particularly in vocational secondary school. To achieve education goal, it is regulated in Standard of Educational National that educators should possess academic qualification and competency as learning agent, physically and mentally health in ability to realize national education goal. The implication of teachers competency which need to be enhanced namely pedagogical, personality, social and professional competency. Teachers' competency and understanding need skill, behavior and professional value . It means that teachers' competency can comprise fact and concept repetition until advance motor skill toward learning behavior and professional value , that competency is one's unique characteristic and the technique of perform and thinking in every situation which is prompted on their skill to use tool and facility in workplace. From this opinion, competency refers to one's performance in a job which can be seen from thinking, attitude and behavior. The enhancement of teachers' competency is a necessity and comprehensive training is needed for each teacher. To develop skill and technology, learning is needed. Teacher can use learning facility to enhance competency test, online teacher education and online performance assessment. It means that teachers should learn in using ICT. Besides, there are three important things which should be thought again concerning education modernization: (a) how we learn (how people learn); (b) what we learn (what people learn); and (c) when and how we learn (how and when people learn). By seeing the answer to three questions, and the potential of ICT which can be exploited as had been explained before, the role of ICT in nation education modernization can be formulated.

Effect of ICT Skills on Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is dynamic and individualistic in nature. The observable varieties between academic staff can reveal their perceptions of the job attributes which is related to the social and economic lifecycle of the individual staff with its related effect on assurance, productivity and job satisfaction. Teacher's commitment and effectiveness are highly dependent on motivation, morale and job satisfaction (Shann, 2001). This indicates that teachers' motivation and job satisfaction are vital phenomena for all type of educational institution. If the teachers are not satisfied with their job, nobody can think about the improvement of performance of the school. If the employees are motivated, they will render their services very efficiently and effectively (Mbua, 2003). It implies that satisfied and motivated school teachers are most likely to affect the students learning positively while the dissatisfied may have negative impacts on students' performance. In spite of altered plans and programs, there is a wide feeling that the teachers are not satisfied in their job as an outcome of which standard of education are decreasing gradually. Job satisfaction consists of total feelings about the nature of job promotion, nature of job, salary, etc. Under such environments it is essential that the proper accepting with reference to satisfaction proceeding from the job life be obtained. According to Sharma and Ghosh (2006) job satisfaction is a complex variable and influenced by some situational factors of the job as well as the dispositional characteristics of the individual. It is also defined as the positive emotional response to the job situation resulting from attaining what the employee wants from the job. Job satisfaction is the general attitude which is determined by the job predictors such as pay, the job itself among other variables. Ifinedo (2003), states that job satisfaction is the level of pleasure on the part of the individual in relation to his or her job. It is frequently defined as the quality of life at work as proficient by the employee with reference to his/her necessities and expectations. Meagan, Kirk and Walter's (2005) defamations of job satisfaction which states that job satisfaction is the combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say; "I am satisfied with my job". Employees with varying ICT skills may exhibit varying attitude to job experiences. Higher levels of ICT skills presumably attract more knowledge and ability, which could contribute significantly to their levels of job performance and satisfaction. Leach and Moon (2008) however conveyed that increased level of ICT skills managed to lower job satisfaction of employees. It appears that staff with a higher level of ICT skills faces a

mismatch between their professional expectations and work realities. On the contrary, Ogugua (2004) revealed that academic staff with sound ICT skills were more productive and satisfied on the job. It is static a delusion as to whether job satisfaction is related to the level of ICT skills controlled by the academic staff.

Review of Literature

Berok and Yunus, (2019) examined a total of 11 English teachers from 6 rural schools in Tatau, Sarawak were selected based on purposive sampling. Data was collected via questionnaire and calculated using percentage. It was then analyzed and semi-structured interview was later conducted. The findings revealed that although teachers, attitude toward ICT integration in rural school was positive and it had enhanced their performance in teaching and learning, the actual use was the practically of integrating ICT. The findings also revealed poor Internet connection, limited facilities and infrastructure were the challenges that had influenced their behavior in using ICT which put a limitation of its usage. Jarrear Ahmad and Mohd, Ahmad Khan (2016) studied “A study of teaching Competency of secondary school teachers in relation to their educational qualifications, streams of type of school”. To study the teaching Competency, 447 secondary school teachers of eastern U.P. is randomly selected. General Teaching Competency scale is a claim observation schedule which has been constructed by Passi and Lalitha to analyze and interpret the data mean, SD and t-test were used between the different demographic variables. There is interesting result drawn from this study that government school teachers are dominating over private teachers in secondary level on the bais of their teaching Competency. It is also found that qualification of secondary school teachers does not have an effect on teaching Competency. The science stream teachers are competent that art stream teachers. Wang Wei et al., (2015), they developed a research model to examine the relationship between employee users’ satisfaction with information and communication technologies (ICT) and job satisfaction. Based on an online survey of 229 employee users of ICT, this study finds that job fit positively moderates the impact of IT satisfaction on job satisfaction. Also, the results approve the mediating effect of both job fit and professional fit. This study contributes to IT performance literature by moving beyond researchers’ focus on IT-related outcomes, such as employee user satisfaction, to broader job-related outcomes.

Methodology

Research Problem

The title of the current study is “Influence of attitude and competency towards ICT on job satisfaction of secondary school teachers”

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the relationship between and among the variables Attitude towards ICT and Competency towards ICT and Job Satisfaction.
- 2) To find out the relationship between and among the variables between Attitude towards ICT and Competency towards ICT and Job Satisfaction of secondary school teachers with respect to
 - a) Types of Institutions
 - b) Medium of Instruction
 - c) Locality

Hypothesis

- 1) There is no significant difference in type of institutions and medium of Instruction, locality with respect to Attitude towards ICTof secondary school teachers.
- 2) There is no significant difference in type of institutions and medium of Instruction,locality with respect to Competency towards ICTof secondary school teachers.
- 3) There is no significant difference in type of institutions and medium of Instruction,locality with respect to Job Satisfactionof secondary school teachers.

Research Methodology

The research technique of study implemented by the investigators for the current study is Normative survey. This method is applied to reach the descriptive sample of data. Sample size: The sample holds of 696 teachers from government, Aided and Un-Aided schools rural and urban area of Thanjavur District. Tools: Attitude, Competency towards Information and Communication Technology questionnaire was designed and standardized by O.Yusuf& R Balogun (2011) Nigerian used for the study. Job satisfaction Inventory was

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constructed by the research scholar and also used for this present study. Variable of the study: The normal variables are used in this study. These study determines to explore this variable with respect to type of institutions, medium of instructions and locality of teachers. Statistical techniques used: The data collected by the research scholar from the sample were evaluated statistically. That the variables were examined by using Descriptive Analysis (Mean, SD) and Differential Analysis ('t'test) to be used.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive Analysis

Table1: Mean and standard Deviation of attitude, competency and job satisfaction towards ICT among secondary school teachers

Variable	Total Score	No.	Mean($\bar{X}$)	Standard deviation(σ)
Attitude	56	696	47.37	4.77
Competency	175		146.52	17.86
Job satisfaction	120		99.53	11.40

Table 2: Mean and standard Deviation of attitude, competency and job satisfaction with respect to demographic variables towards ICT among secondary school teachers

Variable		Types of Institution			Medium of Instruction		Locality	
		Govt.	Aided	un aided	Tamil	English	Rural	Urban
Attitude	No	227	239	230	337	359	354	342
	Mean($\bar{X}$)	47.70	47.37	47.03	47.47	47.27	46.15	48.62
	Standard deviation(σ)	4.63	4.63	5.03	4.52	4.99	5.39	3.62
competency	Mean($\bar{X}$)	145.41	146.43	147.72	144.43	148.49	150.07	143.10
	Standard deviation(σ)	16.71	20.19	16.32	18.88	16.64	10.49	22.31
Job satisfaction	Mean($\bar{X}$)	100.18	99.98	98.41	100.14	98.96	102.37	96.79
	Standard deviation(σ)	11.39	8.97	13.45	11.44	11.35	7.17	13.82

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Mean and standard Deviation of attitude, competency and job satisfaction towards ICT among secondary school teachers

Differential Analysis

Table 3: Shows Mean, SD and 't' Value of competency in ICT among Teachers in digital literacy

Variable		Types of institutions			Medium of instruction		Locality	
		Govt	English	un aided	Tamil	English	Rural	Urban
Attitude	No	227	239	230	337	359	354	342
	Mean($\bar{x}$)	47.70	47.37	47.03	337	359	46.15	48.62
	S D (σ)	4.63	4.63	5.03	47.47	47.27	5.39	3.62
	't' test	0.342			0.565		2.94	
	Signification @ 5% level	NS			NS		S	
competency	Mean($\bar{x}$)	145.41	146.43	147.72	144.43	148.49	150.07	143.10
	S D (σ)	16.71	20.19	16.32	18.88	16.64	10.49	22.31
	't' test	0.378			0.003		1.738	
	Signification @ 5% level	NS			NS		NS	
Job satisfaction	Mean($\bar{x}$)	100.18	99.98	98.41	100.14	98.96	102.37	96.79
	S D (σ)	11.39	8.97	13.45	11.44	11.35	7.17	13.82
	't' test	0.369			0.172		4.766	
	Signification @ 5% level	NS			NS		S	

Findings

There is no significant difference between types of institution in secondary school teachers with respect to attitude, competency towards Information Communication Technology. There is no significant difference between medium of instruction in secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction towards Information Communication Technology. There is significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers with respect to attitude, job satisfaction and no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school teachers with respect to competency towards Information Communication Technology.

Conclusion

This study revealed that majority of the secondary school teachers are at a moderate level of use of ICT. In order to make teachers reach a higher level of use of ICT, there is a need to implement more ICT resources and to provide opportunities to them to utilize and integrate ICT to its fullest potential in their classrooms. It is concluded from the study that there is a positive correlation between use of ICT and all other variables. Efforts of teachers using ICT should be recognized and outstanding achievements of its teachers should be celebrated, so that it increases their self-confidence, attitude and competency towards ICT. Efforts to provide opportunities to attend special awareness programmes of ICT use should be provided to such teachers so that they become technologically competent as well as in job satisfaction also. Since the use of ICT helps to develop leadership qualities and communication skills teachers can encourage the learners to live a better life in the future. Thus efforts should be made by the state and the central government to support teachers in all possible ways to enhance use of ICT in the classrooms.

Reference

- [1] Dr.Shakera Parveen (2018) “Attitude of secondary school teachers towards the usage of technology in classroom”, 2011,5(43), SRJIS ISSN 2278-8808.
- [2] Modesiru, O. Yusuf ., Modupe R. Balogun(2011) ‘Student –Teachers Competence and Attitude towards Information and Communication Technology A Case Study in a Nigerian University Contemporary Educational Technology’, 2011, 2(1), pp 18-36. 2011
- [3] Miro (2018) “Job satisfaction. The case of information technology (IT) professionals in Spain” Universia Business Review ISSN 1698-5117
- [4] Mehmet kemal aydin, Ali Semerci and Mehment Guro, (2016). “Teachers Attitude Towards ICT use in Secondary Schools : A Scale Development Study”. 13th International conference on cognition and exploratory learning in digital age.ISBN: 978-989-8533-55-5, Turkey

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EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTIMEDIA BASED INSTRUCTIONAL PACKAGE FOR ENHANCING LANGUAGE TEACHING SKILLS AMONG PRE -SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract

The present study focuses on Effectiveness of multimedia based instructional package for enhancing language teaching skills among pre -service teachers. The investigator adopted the experimental method for the present study. Pre service teachers in Sivagangai district constitute the sample of the present investigation. As per the objectives framed in the present investigation, the 200 teachers with different variables were selected as a sample of the present study by using purposive sampling technique. A questionnaire with open ended items has been established as a tool for the present study. The measures of central tendency mean and differential studies such as S.D. and 't' – test were used as the statistical techniques for the present study. Then the researcher interpreted the findings and drew a conclusion on the basis of findings.

Introduction

Language is an essential part of In human life. It is the method of communication. It is man's greatest achievement that distinguishes the human being from animals. Language is one of the most important and characteristic forms of human behaviour. In the modern computer world every society today is faced with serious social, economic and political problems. These problems need systematic intelligent and practical solution, for that language is important in the life of any nation as well as that of an individual person. Language is the instrument of the society'. It is used not only for outgoing and incoming information but also for conveying emotions and feelings'. Modern time sare termedasanage of technology. Technology is the application of scientific knowledge to the life. The impact of technology is so tremens ous that dominates the human efforts.

Need and Significant of the Study

English Language teaching skills is very important for the future of the child and national development also believed that English Language teaching skills makes a crucial involvement to a well-formed Education, playing an imperative role in modernization of this society. The present study aims at testing the effectiveness of multimedia based teaching methods method in Indian classrooms which have a particular pattern of imparting English Language teaching skills knowledge. Therefore the present study has focused on teaching of English Language teaching skills by Multimedia Based Instructional package method.

Statement of the Problem

The present Study will attempt to find out the “Effectiveness of Multimedia Based Instructional package for Enhancing Language Teaching skills among Pre -service teachers”

Major Objective of the Study

To find out whether there is significant difference between Pre-test and Post-test mean scores of the Enhancing in English Language teaching skills through multimedia package based.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) There is no significance difference between pre test control and experimental group with pre-service teachers teaching skills in Language through multimedia learning package
- 2) There is no significance difference between post test control and experimental group with pre-service teachers teaching skills in Language through multimedia learning package

Delimitation of the Present Study

- 1) Only Pre -service level is taken for the study.
- 2) Only limited variables were assumed for the study.
- 3) Only Ramanathapuram Educational District is included for the study.

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Review of Related Literature

Madhugupta (2018) investigated “The effect of smart classroom teaching on achievement of teachers”. The findings of the study revealed that i) Main effect of method of teaching, gender and intelligence was found significant on achievement in Social Science among seventh graders ii) The findings of the study further revealed that triple interaction effect of method of teaching, gender and intelligence was found significant on achievement in Social Science among seventh graders. Madhugupta (2019) studied “The opinions of teachers for effectiveness of smart classroom teaching English Language teaching skills for seventh graders”. The analysis disclosed the fact that the smart classroom teaching is highly useful for teachers as well as students. It is very helpful in increasing the achievement level of teachers at their own pace in a motivating and fascinating way in today's competitive education system.

Research Design: In the present study, Experimental research method was adopted for its suitability and accuracy. Two groups of pupils, namely the experimental and control group were taken for the study.

Method Used for the Study: Researcher used Experimental research for this study.

Sample of the study: The investigator selected 200 pre-service teachers for this experiment.

Tools Used for the Study: Language Teaching Skills Multimedia Based Learning Package Hypotheses

Testing

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis :1 There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean score of the enhancing language teaching skills through multimedia package among pre-service teachers

Test	N	Mean	SD	T	Level of Significance
Pre test	30	13.83	2.47	13.02	S
Post test	30	21.10	1.78		

Significant at 0.05 level (2.00) The calculated t^* value (13.02) is higher than the table value at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis: 2 There is no significance difference between pre test experimental group with pre-service teachers teaching skills in Language with respect to gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	15	14.13	2.29	0.65	NS
Female	15	13.53	2.69		

Not Significant at 0.05 level (2.04) The calculated t^* Value (0.65) is less than the table value (2.04) at the 0.05 level of significance. When compared to table value the hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no significant difference between the mean score of Male and Female student in pre test.

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Hypothesis: 3 There is no significance difference between post test experimental group with pre-service teachers teaching skills in Language with respect to gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Male	15	21.33	1.79	0.70	NS
Female	15	20.86	1.80		

Not Significant at 0.05 level (2.04)

The calculated 't' Value (0.70) is less than the table value (2.04) at the 0.05 level of significance. When compare to table value the hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no significant difference between the mean score of Male and Female student in post test.

Hypothesis :4 There is no significant difference between pre test for Enhancing teaching skills of Language with respect to Locality

Locality	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Rural	15	12.73	2.15	2.67	S
Urban	15	14.93	2.34		

Significant at 0.05 level (2.04). The calculated 't' Value (2.67) is greater than the table value (2.04) at the 0.05 level of significance. When compare to table value the hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is significant difference between the mean score of rural and urban student in pre test.

Hypothesis: 5 There is no Significant difference between post test for Enhancing teaching skills of Language with respect to Locality

Locality	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of Significance
Rural	15	20.80	1.56	0.91	NS
Urban	15	21.40	1.99		

Not Significant at 0.05 level (2.04) The calculated 't' Value (0.91) is greater than the table value (2.04) at the 0.05 level of significance. When compare to table value the hypothesis is accepted hence there is no significant difference between the mean score of rural and urban student in post test.

Major Findings of The Study

The following are the findings of the present study: There is a significant difference between pre and post test for pre-service teachers teaching performance of language skills through multimedia based instructional package. There is no significant difference between the mean score of Male and Female student in pre test. The result reveals that the mean score of male (14.13) is higher than the Female (13.53) with respect to their gender. There is no significant difference between the mean score of Male and Female student in post test. The result reveals that the mean score of female (20.86) is higher than the male (21.33) with respect to their gender.

Educational Implication of the Study

The overall results of this study have shown light on the effectiveness of Multimedia Based Instructional package for Enhancing in English Language teaching skills among Pre -service Teachers. This is an encouraging fact that there is bright future for Multimedia Based Instructional package in India to learn English Language teaching skills at B.Ed college level.

Recommendations of the Study

There commendations of the present study are as follows: Multimedia Based Instructional package may be used to learn English Language teaching skills at Pre –service teachers in B.Ed college level. This method may be used to provide equal opportunity in learning irrespective of time, space and person. E-Learning courses for the preparation of Multimedia Based Instructional package should be given to the English Language teaching skills teacher. English Language teaching skills teacher should be trained use the Multimedia Based Instructional package effectively in the classroom.

Suggestions for Further Research

- 1) Studies on effectiveness of Multimedia based Instructional package may be extended too ther subjects.
- 2) Studies on effectiveness of Multimedia based Instructional package maybe extended to other educational levels such as primary, High, Higher Secondary and graduation.
- 3) Studies on effectiveness of Multimedia based Instructional package maybe extended to other districts.

Conclusion

The present study has investigated “The effectiveness of Multimedia based Instructional package for Enhancing in English Language teaching skills among Pre -service teachers”. The study revealed various aspects of dimensions based on place of residence, parent’s Educational qualification and locality and it was found that the effectiveness and utilization were very high in the case of Enhancing in English Language teaching skills.

References

- [1] Bawden(1990).User-oriented evaluation of information services. Aldershot, England: Gower.
- [2] Beydogan, H.Ö.& Hayran,Z. (2015). The effect of multimedia-based learning on the concept of learning levels and attitudes of students. Eurasian Journal of Educational Research, 60, 261-280. <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2015.60.14>
- [3] Carmichael, M., Reid, A-K., & Karpicke, J. D. (2018). Assessing the Impact of Educational Video on Student Engagement, Critical Thinking and Learning: The Current State of Play. A SAGE Whitepaper, SAGE Publishing, 1-21.

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GOLDEN PLUMES FROM YORE: HOLISTIC EDUCATION PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

In the present day children wake up early and race each other to the school. There is an exponential increase of international schools claiming that they are providing holistic learning based on new technologies and differentiated instructional designs depending on the student's propensities. However the aftermath of the pandemic has led to the rise of hybrid schools / colleges country wide and the most glaring issues with this method is the lack of interpersonal communication. To become successful outside the classroom / career there is a requirement for good verbal communication skills and sound core knowledge. Future prospects of our country depend upon the moral values imparted to students during their school/ college life. In this context, there is now a growing demand in education to inculcate, nurture and develop values and ethics, particularly among the youth of the nation. This paper presents a conceptual approach towards creating students with a virtuous integrated personality.

Introduction

In the present day children wake up early and race each other to the school. There is an exponential increase of international schools claiming that they are providing holistic learning based on new technologies and differentiated instructional designs depending on the student's propensities. However the aftermath of the pandemic has led to the rise of hybrid schools / colleges country wide and the most glaring issues with this method is the lack of interpersonal communication. To become successful outside the classroom / career there is a requirement for good verbal communication skills and sound core knowledge. Future prospects of our country depend upon the moral values imparted to students during their school/ college life. In this context, there is now a growing demand in education to inculcate, nurture and develop values and ethics, particularly among the youth of the nation. This paper presents a conceptual approach towards creating students with a virtuous integrated personality.

Teaching / Learning Process

The globe has just come out of the tentacles of a pandemic and with the advent of this virus the nation's education system has gone haywire. Teaching in the post pandemic situation raises issues to instructors and students particularly with regard to five dimensions namely: ease of use and technology know how, viability for academic fraud, ethical issues, economical issues and psychological impact. Higher education leaders need to face the fact that school / college teaching will not continue in the traditional way in the aftermath of the pandemic. We cannot rely on students because they often tend to find easy ways of learning and do not feel guilty for breaking the ethical rule, adopting inappropriate assistance for examinations, and misuse of academic resources. In addition, they are often found lacking in ethical values. While using internet tools continuously, learners tend to break the ethical rules because the act feels less personal as we may not see the other person in actual face to face manner.

Present Scenario

There is a need for new plans to disseminate education because there are explosion of serendipity e – teaching and teachers at all levels. The question that lingers in the mind of educators is whether or not online courses can give students the same discussion rich, well-rounded learning experience as traditional brick and mortar classrooms can. There is a need to design a more flexible education system that works for all students. The serendipity online teaching amplifies issues because it purports complex discourses and multiple relationships crossing physical, cultural and linguistic boundaries. Data of various kinds are automatically recorded in a relatively permanent form and invasion into confidentiality. Educators are under stress and they are coming up with new ways of teaching.

Jumping the Bandwagon

"Holistic education" is a catchword used by the mushrooming institutions for defining a comprehensive approach to teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning form. It is stated that to achieve excellence students have to be taught to reflect on their actions and engage in activities that apply critical-thinking skills toward solving real-world problems. People believe that holistic education is a relatively new movement developed in the 1980s to counteract the

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existing mechanistic learning structures. Several countries are now incorporating holistic goals into their educational system. At the global level this trend is encouraged by the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA, Department of Education, 2017).

Golden Plumes from Yore

Taking the best principles of education advocated by our tradition and blending it in the modern context will help us to reform education. The reforms will enable us to bridge the gap between the haves and have not and prevent the mushrooming growth of expensive microschools. By integrating the lessons learned from our ancient texts, coupled with the available modern online tools, we can provide accessible, relevant, customized, equitable and value based education for the children in remote parts of India. In India, both formal and informal ways of education system existed down history. Indigenous education was imparted at home, in temples, pathshalas, tols, chatuspadis and gurukuls and at later stages in pialsalso. Education based on a person's entire experience has roots in ancient concepts of instruction. The oriental heritage system in India laid stress on two kinds of knowledge namely knowledge of this world and the other world. The great epic presents a model for the teacher and the pupil.

This is evident from the discussion between lord Krishna and Dhrona Acharya on the 15th day of the Mahabaratha war. The great epic presents us a model where the guru identifies the innate skill of his pupils and primes them. It was the guru who decided mastering the mace for Bhima and Duryodhana and archery for Arjuna. Thus the concept of judging different learning styles was prevalent in the days of yore. Ekalavya, approached Guru Dronacharya for archery training but the opportunity was denied on account of the social situation of the milieu. Undaunted, Ekalavya learned in his own way seeking inspiration from the Guru's image, and he emerged as one of the finest archers of his time. This is the basic concept of distance education and mentoring system where physical separation or distance between the teacher and the learner, has been having its roots in India.

This basic concept has extended its dimensions and has grown in the form stand-alone learning content or one to one to one training methods in the present day. The concept of visiting faculty was present in the ancient Indian education system as scholars like Huen Tsang and Pythagoras came to India to understand the methods of learning. The Nalanda University had a long and illustrious life for 800 years from the fifth to the twelfth century. It was a completely residential university believed to have 2,000 teachers and 10,000 students. The architectural components reveal the holistic nature of knowledge that was sought and imparted at this university. It suggests a seamless co-existence between nature and man, and between living and learning. In India's Gurukul education, stories and parables brought out real-life learning while reducing monotony for students. Panchatantra is an outstanding example of philosophical teachings given through parables. This can be compared to case studies in the modern garb. Once again iterating to the discussion between Krishna and Dhrona, the question asked by Krishna, was "Did you spend your entire life, all your learnings, all your tapasya for your son? Does your life has no other significance? The knowledge that you have acquired, was it only for your son? Was nothing meant for the welfare of human kind? Tell me o great sage Dronacharya, did your life had any other objective...?"

In continuation Krishna says "you should have taught your own son how to make correct decisions. You should have taught Aswathama how to differentiate between decisions that are morally correct and morally wrong. Did you teach Aswathama the knowledge of Dharma? We all know what you did with Eklavya, you demanded his right thumb? You demanded the thumb of a talented archer because you were insecure towards your pupils and your own son. Was that morally correct gurudev? Had you taught your son some morality, he would not have fought against Dharma in the camp of Duryodhana. Look at Yuyutsu, he is the son of king Dhritarashtra and Sauvali (a royal servant maid) but he is fighting from the side of Dharma. With your imagined definition of success destroyed the Dharma of your child. You taught him Greed, avarice, wrath, fear and insecurity. You never became a "Guru", you were always a "Father" to your son. A real "Guru" is that person who donates Education. He does not "trade" education. A person who has ego, greed, wrath, anger and jealousy in his heart, he can never be a Guru." Thus the basic tenets of a teacher is set as an example.

Devising a Holistic Education Model

The goal of holistic education is to cultivate a developing child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual attributes. Nurturing the whole child means providing opportunities that are personalized to a child's skills and feelings. The traditional Indian systems have stipulated learning conditions for the whole child that lives within the interconnected environment including home, school, and society. These systems can cater to the present scenario, where the market is flooded with multimedia resources, internet, portable devices and platforms. Evaluation of curricular, social and emotional development can be measured easily to

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improve upon equity and outcomes. Teachers must be prepared to nurture students with varying educational levels and learning capabilities. Present day education has to devise models including experiential learning, self- paced learning, and community learning. The teacher strategies should include: strong student-teacher relationships, encourage self-confidence and emotional reflection.

Hybrid Holistic Model

Conclusion

Holistic education is based on a learning philosophy that brings a number of benefits to students, teachers, schools, and the society. Students are empowered to improve their educational outcomes and gain the life skills necessary to take on a successful profession. The nation's education system requires better plans than serendipities and juggling of adhoc measures. Educators should do more than using technology to engage students, particularly with regard to priming them as virtuous integrated personalities. It is time for both parents and educators to come to grips with this new reality and come up with complementary efforts to make the best out of the situation. Teachers play the central role in enacting learning policies, and they have the greatest opportunity to help students discover their talents and leverage on the community and world.

References

- [1] Anderson, R.K.; Boaler, J.; Dieckmann, J.A. (2018). Achieving Elusive Teacher Change through Challenging Myths about Learning: A Blended Approach. *Educ. Sci.* 8, no. 3: 98.
- [2] Beavis, Adrian(2004), Why Parents Choose Public or Private Schools. [://www.researchgate.net/publication/241801252](http://www.researchgate.net/publication/241801252)
- [3] Bernard E. Whitley (1998) Factors Associated with Cheating Among College Students: A Review. *Research in Higher Education* 39, 235–274
- [4] Bhavana.AR.(2020) Serendipity E –Teaching: Problems and Perspectives, Developing the Next Generation Learners in this Digital Era(Vol. I)
- [5] Devin K. JOSHI (2021) Humanist but not radical: The educational philosophy of Thiruvalluvar Kural , Singapore Management University Institutional Knowledge at Singapore Management University, Research Collections (I)
- [6] Fass, R. A. (1990) Cheating and plagiarism. *Ethics and Higher Education*. May, W. W. editor. New York: Macmillan Publishing Company and American Council on Education.
- [7] Tim Brown(2019). *Change by Design*, Harper Collins UK

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION THROUGH LIFE SKILLS WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS

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Abstract

Outcome Based Education (OBE) is an innovative approach which helps in expanding the development horizons of education. Life skills are skills that enable individuals to deal effectively with the challenges of everyday life. Problem-Solving is an ability to comprehend what the goal of the problem is and what rules could be applied to represent the key for solving that problem. While solving any problem one must be systematic and logical in their approach. Problem solving approach is a process where one uses their previous knowledge and skills according to their own understanding in unfamiliar situations. Problem solving skill, which is a strategy where the student acquires new knowledge during the process of resolving problems, is an approach in implementing OBE.

Key words: *Problem Solving Skills, Outcome-Based Education, Life Skills. Professional Skills.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization, traditional education system is losing its relevance. In today's world, everything changes very rapidly and continuously. More skills are required to work with galloping technology. The educational institutions ought to produce graduates to cope with technological development. Thus, to overcome the requirement, it is mandatory to shift from traditional education system to Outcome Based Education (OBE). Outcome-based education (OBE) is an educational delivery model that focuses on mapping, measuring, and achieving predetermined educational goals to help students learn, develop, and nurture skills that would help them grow in their professional life as well as personal life. The ability to solve problems is a basic life skill and is essential to our day-to-day lives, at home, at school, and at work. We solve problems every day without really thinking about how we solve them. Problem solving is the process of identifying a problem, developing possible solution paths, and taking the appropriate course of action.

Outcome Based Education

Outcome-based education is a system where all the parts and aspects of education are focused on the outcomes of the course. The students take up courses with a certain goal of developing skills or gaining knowledge and they have to complete the goal by end of the course. There is no specific style or time limit of learning. The learner can learn as per their choice. The faculty members, moderators, and instructors guide the students based on the target outcomes. A renowned academician and educational psychologist, William G. Spady, best known as the "Father of Outcome-Based Education" had coined the term "OBE" in the year 1988. A sociologist who innovated Outcome Based Education, Spady (1994) ruled out spelling out the objectives for this student-centred approach. Rather he outlined the following ground principles for his Outcome-Based Approach which is worth perusing.

Problem Solving Skills

According to some Kepner-Tregoe, problem solving is the main idea of human evolution. Problem solving abilities will make it possible to them to keep thriving. That is why an effective problem solving becomes important not only in working situation but also in the setting of daily life. Problem-solving skills are skills that help us to spot and solve problems efficiently and effectively. Although problem-solving is often identified as its own separate skill, other related skills contribute to this aptness. Some prime problem-solving skills include Active listening, Analysis, Research, Creativity, Communication, Dependability, Decision making, Team building, and Self-reliance. Good problem-solving skills empower us not only in our personal life but are critical in our professional life. In the current fast-changing global economy, employers often identify everyday problem solving as crucial to the success of their organizations. For learners, problem solving can be used to develop practical and creative solutions, and to show independence and initiative.

Steps Involved In OBE Based Problem Solving Skills

Outcome based educational problem-solving skills include some basic procedures mentioned below:

- 1) Identifying the problem – Before getting too far, it is to be better to understand which kind of problem we are having.
- 2) Defining the problem – What comes next as the team problem solving strategies is to define the problem. If the previous step resembles to learning the situation, this procedure equals to writing down what the true problem is. Doing so will help us to further understand what actions we need to take.
- 3) Exploring the problem – In this procedure, you are required to dig deeper what is causing the problem. By understanding what is there to fix, we can define what actions we need to take to start and then fix.
- 4) Start taking action – After we list down what the problems are and what actions we can take to resolve the problem, do what we can do. It is better to be done as soon as possible than making the problems getting unresolved. Or, getting bigger.
- 5) Always look back – Once we have done what we can do in terms of resolving the problem, it's time to evaluate our self.

Benefits of OBE Based Problem - Solving Skills

We can benefit many things from learning OBE based problem solving skills. Several benefits that we can get from that can be listed as follows: We can make our self more sensitive in terms of identifying problem. We will be used to brainstorm while thinking about any possible solutions. We experience transparency and flexibility. We may also get trained for testing the solutions first before implementing it wholly. By keeping the habit of 'always look back', we will learn that it is important to analyse results. We can realise the self-development and career progression.

Conclusion

Problem-solving skills are important in every career at every level. As a result, effective problem solving may also require job-specific technical skills. Problem solving is the process of constructing and applying mental representations of problems to finding solutions to those problems that are encountered in nearly every context. Outcomes based education (OBE) is the highlighted trend these days in education area to manual students in their professional career and lead them too greater informed and creative. Thus, outcome-based education is that desired outcomes form the basis for the entire learning system.

Reference

- [1] Michael J. Lawson and Helen Askell-Williams, "Outcomes-based education", discussion paper, 2007
- [2] Spady, William G. Outcome-Based Education: Critical Issues and Answers
- [3] Bransford, J., & Stein, B. S. (1984). The IDEAL problem solver: A guide for improving thinking, learning, and creativity. New York: WH Freeman.
- [4] Harden RM, Crosby JR, Davis MH. An introduction to outcome-based education. Med Teacher 21(1), 1999.

ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AT COLLEGIATE LEVEL

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Abstract

Language is a complex whole, the mastery of which requires the learner's total commitment for life. English has become an important tool to participate in international communication and competition. Therefore, it is required to improve the ability of English Teaching in order to meet the needs of the development of the country. Therefore, the use of effective teaching methods and the improvement of the students' English learning effect are very important. However, how to effectively implement English Teaching in college and how to improve college students' English proficiency through teaching have become an urgent problem to be solved. This paper analysed the problems existing in College English teaching, and puts forward a variety of methods to promote college English teaching effect, which can be used as a reference for college English teaching. English Language Teaching (ELT) includes various approaches, techniques and methods that are involved in teaching English, to people with English as First Language and also those who use it as a second and a foreign language. The goal of language acquisition is communicative competence, which is the ability to use the language correctly and appropriately to achieve communication goals. 'Communicative competence is made up of four competence areas: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse and strategic.

Keywords: *English Language Teaching, Importance of English Language Teaching*

Introduction

Language is a complex whole, the mastery of which requires the learner's total commitment for life. The person's prior knowledge, attitudes, personality, learning styles, skills and motivation are all factors related to eventual outcome of the language study (Brown, 2004). Language, so far as we know, is something specific to humans, that is to say it is the basic capacity that distinguishes humans from all other living beings. Language therefore remains potentially a communicative medium capable of expressing ideas and concepts as well as moods, feelings and attitudes. English language comes to our aid in our commercial transactions throughout the globe. English is the language of the latest business management in the world and Indian proficiency in English has brought laurels to many Indian business managers. English is a means not only for international commerce; it has become increasingly essential for inter-state commerce and communication. English has today become one of the major languages of the world, it will be very difficult to neglect English language because of rich literature, scientific and technical nature of language. English is accepted as the second language in India. In the words of Gandhi, "English is a language of international commerce, it is the language of diplomacy and it contains many a rich literary treasure". It gives us an introduction that English has occupied an important place in Indian education. Therefore, English occupies an important place in the school curriculum and works as a powerful language of communication to provide a strong binding force to keep all the diverse groups united.

English as a Difficult Language for Indian Students

English language is not difficult but Indian students think that English is a foreign language and that is very difficult language to learn. Knowledge of English is necessary if one wants to come up in life. It is major window of the modern world. Another challenging factor is students' beliefs about the nature of learning English as a subject consisting of a list of words and a set of grammatical rules which are to be memorized and separable skills to be acquired rather than a set of integrated skills and sub skills the students in English classes do not have common background knowledge because some of them are trained in rural areas in which un-qualified English teachers teach them. While some of the students take advantage of using satellite programs, As classes are crowded, most of the students do not have enough practice in English and do not overcome language learning problems and are not proficient enough to communicate in the foreign language. Because in the limited hours of instruction, they normally could not have the chance of learning English especially the most favoured skills of listening and speaking is no place for group work discussion. To acquire the target language effectively, learners need to engage actively in processing the meanings of whatever they hear and read. Group work in the educational context generally involves a small number of students working together to achieve a task.

English Language Teaching-Meaning

English Language Teaching (ELT) includes various approaches, techniques and methods that are involved in teaching English, to people with English as First Language and also those who use it as a second and a foreign language.

Basic concepts in English Language Teaching

The goal of language acquisition is communicative competence, which is the ability to use the language correctly and appropriately to achieve communication goals. ' Communicative competence is made up of four competence areas: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse and strategic. The first language or mother tongue of a speaker is known as L1 and the second language of a speaker is known as L2 in ELT and Linguistics.

Objectives of Teaching and Learning in English

- 1) To develop necessary language skills.
- 2) To enable teachers and students to interact meaningfully in available and given situations in various life contexts.
- 3) To develop conversational skills.
- 4) To develop proficiency in English for learning other knowledge-subjects.
- 5) To develop confidence and competence in order to perform effectively and efficiently in real life situations.
- 6) To enable students to acquire the phatic use of the language for good manners and right expressions on various occasions and in life situations.

Importance English Language Teaching and Learning at Collegiate Level

- 1) Perfect communication – It is important to speak effectively. People get impressed by those who have good communication skills.
- 2) Gain Confidence – good communication skills gain our confidence
- 3) Achieve our goal early – Effective English language skills help us to meet our career goals quickly.
- 4) Effective personality – When we speak effectively and with confidence, anyone can get attracted.
- 5) Part of the Global community – English language is a part of the global world. So, if one knows good English then one can interact with others.
- 6) Multiple Career Prospects – A person possessing effective communication skills have more career opportunities than others.

Methods for Enhancing English Language Teaching at Collegiate Level

Layered Teaching Method

Layered teaching method is aimed at different English level and different learning ability of students with different English teaching methods. Layered teaching, as one of the effective measures for quality-teaching, is teaching students in accordance with their aptitude (Wang, 2010) . The issue satisfies the individual's difference sufficiently and develops the character of each student. Practice has proved that the method not only can effectively improve the academic performance of students, and significantly reduced the rate of poor students, effectively improve the colleges and universities present English teaching level. Before the implementation of layered teaching, we must meet the requirements of two aspects: first, has a comprehensive grasp to the students' English level; second, in the aspect of English teaching materials selection, to combine the students' English level. Therefore, in the process of implementing English teaching, the college can refer to the layered teaching method.

Life-Related Teaching Method

Life-related teaching method refers to integrate English teaching into life, learn English in life, master the basic skills of English in practice. Life-related teaching is an English teaching which is based on life. It is different from the traditional teaching methods in the selection of teaching materials, teaching process and teaching effect. life-related teaching is to let students learn English out of class, and to learn English in practice. Life-related teaching method breaks the traditional English teaching mode, and the students are liberated from the shackles of the traditional English teaching, which makes the students actively integrate into the teaching. Life-related teaching puts forward higher requirements to English teachers' teaching level and teaching theory (Xu, 2010) . In the teaching level, it requires teachers to have a deep understanding of the teaching content, select the appropriate

teaching material from life, and introduce the life material into the practical English teaching. In the aspect of teaching theory, the traditional English teaching pays attention to the training of students' vocabulary, grammar and sentence pattern, and the English teachers only need to master the theoretical knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, sentence patterns and so on. The life-related teaching attaches great importance to cultivate the students' comprehensive ability in our daily life, which requires the English teachers to master rich English teaching theory. Therefore, in the process of implementing English teaching, the college can refer to the life-related teaching method.

Task-Based Teaching Method

Task-based teaching method is to cultivate students' confidence in learning English through the gradual accumulation of the task. Task-based English teaching method is based on the task of the basic module, in the process of English teaching, to complete a series of tasks. In this process, English teachers and students can get along very well, and English teachers and students will be able to speak English in a real environment, to improve students' ability of English communication. Task-based teaching method compares with the traditional English teaching has the following advantages: first, task-based English teaching method has a very clear teaching goal; Second, the task-based teaching method is a kind of student-centered English teaching methods; Third, task-based teaching method is carried out around the students, each student has a certain task, prompting students to actively participate in the teaching of English. Task-based English teaching method not only put forward higher requirements to the English teachers in colleges and universities, but also put forward higher requirements to the students. In the aspect of English teachers, task-based teaching method requires English teachers to have a high comprehensive quality and strong professional knowledge, in the process of task allocation, to pay attention to the difficulty of the task. In the aspect of students, the task-based English teaching method requires that each student has a certain task, and everyone can't be lazy. Therefore, in the process of implementing English teaching, the college can refer to the task-based teaching method.

Group-Divided and Cooperative Teaching Method

Group-divided and cooperative teaching method is according to the interests and the English levels, divide students into groups. Each group as a small team, English teachers' teaching according to the actual situation of each team, at the same time, the requirement between team members, learn from each other, communicate with each other. According to the English teachers' teaching method, choose the appropriate method of learning English. On the one hand, group-divided and cooperative learning can enhance students' sense of team cooperation. On the other hand, it can improve students' ability to communicate in English quickly. Group-divided and cooperative teaching method is based on students' autonomous learning. In the process of English teaching, through the communication between the team members, stimulate students' interest in learning English, mobilize the enthusiasm and initiative of the students to learn English. In the process of group-divided and cooperative teaching, not only can strengthen students' team cooperation consciousness and responsibility, but also can achieve a comprehensive and sustainable development of students' learning English. Therefore, in the process of implementing English teaching, the college can refer to the group-divided and cooperative teaching method.

Community Language Learning

Community Language Learning (CLL) also known as Counseling Language Learning, is an approach in which learners work together to develop what aspects of a language they would like to learn. The teacher acts as a counsellor and paraphraser, while the learner acts as a collaborator. This method was developed by Charles A. Curran, a specialist in counseling and psychology. It was created especially for Adult learners who might fear to appear foolish; so the teacher becomes a language counselor, understands them and leads them to overcome their fears. Its base is Krashen's Monitor Theory (Affective Filter Hypothesis) and the Cognitive Theory where the human mind is active, as opposed to Behaviourism, where learning is merely a response to a stimulus.

Suggestopaedia

A teaching method developed by the Bulgarian psychotherapist Georgi Lozanov, Suggestopaedia applies "positive suggestion" in teaching. The name is derived from "suggestion" and "pedagogy". It is based on Suggestology, a psychological theory that says human beings respond to subtle clues of which they are not consciously aware of. The main principles of Suggestopaedia are

- 1) learners will use their hidden potential only when they feel relaxed and happy
- 2) Harmonious collaboration of the conscious and the unconscious

- 3) The most conspicuous characteristics of Suggestopaedia are the decoration, furniture and arrangement of the classroom, the use of music and the authoritative behaviour of the teacher.

Advantages of English Language Teaching

The Ability to Communicate in a New Language: While it might seem obvious, the main benefit a person gains when they commit to learning English, or any language is the ability to use that language to communicate with other speakers of that language and use it to create connections with a wider range of people. **The Brain Undergoes a Change in Electrical Activity:** According to a 2010 study, "The Contribution of Multilingualism to Creativity," learning a new language increases electrical activity in the brain, even at the earliest stages of language learning. These new neural pathways allow a person to enhance their mental flexibility, which is particularly important in keeping the brain healthy. In effect, language learning helps exercise the brain to keep it flexible and agile. **Increased Problem-Solving Abilities:** Learning a new language is essentially one big problem-solving exercise. Language learners benefit from increased problem-solving abilities in all of the following areas:

- 1) Abstract thinking skills
- 2) Concept formation
- 3) Creative hypothesis formulation
- 4) Strengthened capacity to identify, understand and solve problems
- 5) The ability to focus on a task by filtering out distractions and extraneous information
- 6) An increase in multi-tasking ability

Greater Comprehension for How Language Works and Is Used: The acquisition of a second language benefits a person by creating a greater comprehension of how language works and is used. This means that not only are multilingual people better able to better read and interpret social situations, they are also able to learn new languages, even non-verbal ones like computer coding, faster than monolingual people

Conclusion

The goal of English Teaching in colleges and universities is to cultivate students' English practical ability and intercultural communicative competence through the use of effective English teaching methods. In order to improve the present situation of the current college English teaching methods, promote the reform of English teaching methods, improve teaching quality, colleges and universities should attach importance to reform of college English teaching, and actively promote the implementation of university teaching methods, to provide a good external environment for the reform of College English teaching.

References

- [1] Akesson, K., Dreinhofer, K. E., & Woolf, A. D. (2003). Improved Education in Musculoskeletal Conditions Is Necessary for All Doctors. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 81, 677-683.
- [2] Almoallim, H., Bukhari, E., Amasaib, W., & Zaini, R. (2012). How to Avoid Delay in SLE Diagnosis and Management. In H. Almoallim (Ed.), *Systemic Lupus Erythematosus* (pp. 219-242). Croatia: InTech. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/26498>
- [3] Al-Nammari, S. S., James, B. K., & Ramachandran, M. (2009). The Inadequacy of Musculoskeletal Knowledge after Foundation Training in the United Kingdom. *The Bone and Joint Journal*, 19, 1413-1418. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1302/0301-620x.91b11.22445>
- [4] Wang, X. J. (2010). Investigation and Analysis of the Burnout Status of College Female English Teachers. *Journal of Jinan Vocational College*, 1, 37-38, 41.
- [5] Xu, H. Y. (2010). A Study of University English Teachers' Professional Weariness. *Education and Modernization*, 3, 88-91.
- [6] Xiaona Dong (2016) Research on the Teaching Methods of College English"written by Xiaona Dong, published by Creative Education, Vol.7 No.9, 2016

INTEGRATING LIFE SITUATION IN TEACHING NEED BASED CONCEPTS TO ENHANCE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS AMONG STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The study aims to find out the effectiveness of Integrating Life Situations in Teaching Need-based concepts in English Speaking Skills among Secondary School students. The objectives of the study are to identify the Need-Based Speaking Skills in English among Secondary School Students. To design and plan the Teaching-Learning Activities in English for the students in Integrating Life Situational Teaching to enhance English Speaking Skills among Secondary School students. To find out the level of effect on English teaching by Integrating different Life Situations to enhance English Speaking Skills among Secondary School students. The investigator adopted a True experimental Design. In True experimental Design, the investigator adopted a Pre-test - Post-test Control group design for the study. The investigator used a Convenient Sampling Technique for selecting the samples for the study. The investigator selected 80 homogeneous samples by making use of the selective procedures of Statistical Matching and Random assignment. In the control group, 40 samples are selected and in the experimental group, 40 samples are selected therefore 80 students are selected by the investigator to implement Integrating Life Situations in enhancing Speaking Skills in English. The investigator used Descriptive Analysis by using the measures of Mean and Standard Deviation. The investigator used the 't' test to identify the significant difference between the variables. Findings of the study revealed that students' performance in Speaking Skills of students in both Traditional Methods of Teaching and Integrated Life Situational Teaching method is found the same. The students learn Speaking Skills in the Integrated Life Situations Teaching Method than the Traditional Method of classroom teaching. Experimental Group students achieve high performance of Speaking Skills in English because Integrated Life Situational teaching enhancing their Speaking Skills in English. Students enhanced their Speaking Skills in English through Integrating Life Situations. In Integrating Life Situational Teaching, students easily and interestingly involve Teaching-Learning Process.

Keywords: *English Language Teaching, Integrating Life Situation, English Speaking Skills.*

Introduction

English Language is considered as an International Language. It is spoken in many countries. It is an important second language in many parts of the world including India. Now days English has become the common man's language. It is taught in the schools in almost every country on this earth. It is a vehicle for communicating scientific and technological information. In Indian Education System, India followed three-language formula. In Tamil Nadu Education system, they follow two-language formula. In Tamilnadu, Government schools most of the students are socially, economically, educationally backward and first-generation learners. Tamil Nadu Government has taken several efforts to improve the standard of teaching and learning English in various ways. Also, Innovative Language Teaching methods have been implemented in Government schools. But the achievement of the students in English Language Skills are not up to the expected level.

Importance of English Language

English language has been playing an important role both in our educational system and in our national life. In the pre-independence India, English was the language of administration, a compulsory subject at the schools and colleges levels, and the medium of instruction for some subjects at the school and college, and for all subjects at the university level. But still English occupies an important place in our educational system and life of our country. It occupies an important place in courts, commerce and industries. Besides being a link and library language in India, it is a major window to the modern world. Under such circumstances, it is impossible for us neglect the study of English. Just after independence, the primary of English was subjected to series of challenges from some of our own people. These people advocated that English language should quit India along with the rulers. But today, English is once again on the progressive curve in our country. It plays an important role in India's national life and educational system.

Curriculum Framework and its contributions in English Language Teaching

Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has stressed that Secondary Education is a crucial stage in the educational hierarchy as it prepares the students for higher education and also the world of work. Therefore, at this stage of school education, good command over the English language is essential. At the end of secondary level, students should attain a good working knowledge of English. However, the methodology adopted in the English classrooms has played an important role. Further the above statements strongly supported by the Report of the Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) and also it witnessed that the innovative methodology must be adopted in the enhancement of Listening Speaking Reading and Writing skills of the English Language. The commission further included that all students may not become eloquent speakers or good stylists but if proper methods such as situated and simulated teaching and learning and structure based teaching are adopted, every normal student should be able to learn to speak and write intelligibly. It is supported by the conceptual ideas of National Curriculum Framework (2005) it rightly pointed out that curriculum must connect knowledge to life outside the school, ensuring that learning shifts away from rote methods and enriching the curriculum must be beyond textbooks. It also said that Syllabi and textbooks should enable the teacher in organising classroom experiences in consonance with the child's nature and environment, and thus providing opportunities for all children. In Language education it emphasised the three-language formula includes proficiency in English. It further stated that Reading and writing, listening and speech, contribute to the child's progress in all curricular areas and must be the basis for curriculum planning. Emphasis on reading throughout the primary classes is necessary to give every child a solid foundation for school learning. Further the framework revealed that the importance of English language in the following words, It quoted that English in India is a global language in a multilingual country. A variety and range of English teaching situations prevail here owing to the twin factors of teacher proficiency in English and pupils' exposure to English outside schools. Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA 2016) framed and implemented new remedial teaching and various techniques in English Language Teaching in order to enhance English Language Skills among the students. Teachers are trained to teach English properly as a language. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2020) stated that, English language policies must be realistic. The primary means of English language curriculum for the students of higher secondary level is

- 1) To develop the communication competence in English with understanding and clarity on the basis of everyday situations.
- 2) To cultivate the aural skills to understand the formal and informal expressions, and includes the understanding of the language spoken at the regular speed.
- 3) To develop the aptitude to grasp various sorts of materials at sensible speed.
- 4) To improve the capacity to express his/her thoughts precisely and informally in composed English. To attain the objectives overhead, it is essential to use the prescribed reading materials used in the class.

Importance of Speaking Skill

Languages had their origins in the speech. A person may not know to read and write in mother tongue but can very well communicate through speaking. Speaking is considered the most important of the four language skills of English. Speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real life situations. Excellence in speaking Skills of English language is the most prominent one for effective communication. English is universally recognized as a means of communication in the world, students must enhance good speaking skill along with the other skills. If speaking skills are worked upon it has a positive effect on other language skills also as all the skills are interrelated. The grammatical rules of a language is not sufficient enough for the effective use of the language for speaking. To develop oral skills in the English language, the students should have an acceptable pronunciation, intonation and knowledge of conversational English. **For Segura (2012)**, the speaking skill is commonly considered to be the most significant skill of four existing in a language. Although this skill is the most significant to develop in learners, it is ludicrous to think about the fact that learners usually spend years in a classroom trying to learn the language; yet, they have not been successful to speak it properly. **Patteti (2014)** gave a list of the following sub-skills of speaking skill.

- 1) Pronounce the distinctive sounds of a language clearly
- 2) Use stress and rhythmic patterns and intonation patterns of the language clearly
- 3) Using grammatically correct form of the words
- 4) Grammatically correct framing of the sentences

- 5) Appropriate usage of the vocabulary
- 6) Using the language appropriate to the situation

Advantages of Integration of Life Situation in Teaching English

- 1) It attracts learners' attention and increase their language learning motivation
- 2) It draws on social capacities of learners which are useful in language learning
- 3) It helps with developing and improving communicative and pragmatic competencies in language
- 4) It creates a meaningful language learning environment
- 5) It indulges the creative side into the traditional language learning process;
- 6) It reinforces a positive and interactive language learning atmosphere;
- 7) It bridges the gap between language learning theories and actual
- 8) It reinforces a contextualized acquisition of new language items
- 9) It connects linguistic forms and structures with real-life uses
- 10) It helps students feel relaxed and at ease while learning
- 11) It widens and expands learners' horizons
- 12) It adds fun and joy to language learning
- 13) It turns the language learning process into a contextualized process;
- 14) It helps learners realize learning goals and objectives;
- 15) It helps learners with sharing and employing their linguistic input;
- 16) It reinforces reflection on one's own learning;
- 17) It attracts learners' attention.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To identify the Need-Based Speaking Skills in English among Secondary School students.
- 2) To design and plan the Teaching-Learning Activities in English for the students in Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method to enhance English Speaking Skills among Secondary School students.
- 3) To find out the level of effect on English teaching by Integrating different Life Situations to enhance English Speaking Skills among Secondary level students.

Operational Definition of Key Terms

Integrating Life Situations

Integrating Life Situations are real-life situations that are created by the investigator in the natural environment which is suitable for teaching English Speaking Skills.

Teaching

Instruction process of Teaching English Speaking Skills by integrating different real-life Situations.

Need-Based Concepts

It indicates the essential concepts in English Speaking Skills for Secondary School students.

English Speaking Skills

English Speaking Skills of Secondary School students such as the ability to speak fluently, using appropriate vocabulary in speaking, expressions, and use of Phonological skill in speaking.

Students

9th standard Students studying from Government Higher Secondary School, Kalayarkovil, Sivagangai District

Secondary School

It indicates the level of Education I which comes before Higher Secondary Level and after Elementary Level.

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Hypotheses

- 1) There is a low level of performance in English Speaking Skills among Secondary School Students in English.
- 2) Integrating Life Situational Teaching enhances Speaking Skills in English among Secondary School students.
- 3) There exists no significant difference between the Pre-test mean scores of Control and Experimental group students Speaking skills in English.
- 4) There exists a significant difference between the Post-test mean scores of Control and Experimental group students Speaking skills in English.

Methodology

The researcher adopted the True Experimental Design. In True experimental Design the investigator adopted Pre-test - Post-test Control group design. Sampling Technique: In educational researches, a sampling technique is used to collect a sample from the target population. Selected samples are representative one which represents the entire population or it is a small piece of population obtained by a probability process. The investigator used Convenient Sampling Technique for selecting the samples for the study. The investigator selected 80 homogeneous samples by making use of the selective procedures of statistical matching and Random assignment. In the Control group, 40 samples are selected and in the experimental group, 40 samples are selected therefore 80 students are selected by the investigator to implement Integrating Life Situations in enhancing Listening Skills in English. Research Tool: Speaking Skill-Check List was used by the investigator. Speaking Skill-Checklist contains two parts. The first part of the Speaking Skill-Check list is about (1) The respondents' personal Information like gender, residing area of the students, Education qualification of the parents, and occupation of the parents, (2) The second part contains items related to Speaking Skill and its Sub skills such as Phonological Skill, Vocabulary Skill, Grammar Skill, Expression Skill, and Fluency.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The statistical techniques of Differential Analysis are used to analysed the data. The investigator used Descriptive Analysis by using the measures of Mean and Standard Deviation. The investigator used a t-test to identify the significant difference between the variables.

Table 5.23: Significance of Mean difference between the Control Group and Experimental Group Students in Pre-testing condition and Post -testing Condition of overall Speaking Skills in English Language.

S. No	Group	Pre-testing condition		'r'- value	t- value	Post-testing condition		'r' value	't' - value
		Mean	SD			Mean	SD		
1.	Control Group	3.78	0.800	0.308	***	11.38	1.102	0.120	* 43.767
2.	Experimental Group	3.73	1.198		0.260	21.68	1.141		
df =78 * 1% Significant Level ** 5% Significant Level *** Not Significant Level									

The above table reveals that the Pre - testing condition of Control Group and Experimental Group as well as the Post - testing condition of Control Group and Experimental Group in enhancing Speaking Skills in English Language through Traditional Method of Teaching and Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method.

The following conclusions are drawn from the above table. In Pre - testing condition the performance of the students in Speaking Skill of English Language of Control Group and Experimental Group do not have significant difference, Whereas in Post - testing condition both Experimental Group and Control Group gained improvement in Speaking Skills because of Traditional Method and Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method. But the Experimental Group Students performance is better in using Speaking skills in English than the Control Group Students. (**'t'-value = *43.767**, Significance at 1% Level). This shows that the changes in the Performances in Speaking Skills of English Language among students of both Control Group and Experimental Group varies because of the effect of Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method.

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Table 5.24: Significance of Mean difference between Control Group and Experimental Group Students in Pre-testing condition and Post - testing condition in Speaking skills of English Language.

S. No	Testing condition	Control Group		'r' value	't'-value	Experimental Group		'r' value	't' -value
		Mean	SD			Mean	SD		
1	Pre testing condition	3.78	0.800	0.098	* 37.062	3.73	1.102	-.161	* 63.693
2.	Post testing Condition	11.38	1.198			21.68	1.141		
df= 78 * 1% Significant Level ** 5% Significant Level *** Not Significant Level									

The above table reveals that the Pre - testing and Post - testing condition of Control Group as well as Pre - testing and Post - testing condition of Experimental Group in enhancing Speaking Skills in English Language through Traditional Method of Teaching and Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method. The following conclusions are drawn from the above table. There is significant mean difference between Pre - testing and the Post - testing condition of Control Group students in Speaking Skills of English Language through Traditional Method of Teaching. (**'t'-value = *37.062**). There is significant mean difference between Pre - testing and the Post - testing condition of Experimental Group Students in Speaking Skills of English Language through Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method. (**'t'-value = *63.693**). In Post-testing condition the Experimental Group students achieve high Performance in Speaking Skills of English Language, because Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method enhancing their Speaking Skills in English.

Findings of the Study

In Pre-testing condition Control group and Experimental group Student's performance in Speaking Skills of English Language is found in same. In Post-testing condition Control group and Experimental group Student's performance in Speaking Skills having significant differences. Experimental group students' performance is better than the Control group students in Speaking Skills of English Language. The Experimental group students learn Speaking Skills in English Language through Integrated Life Situations Teaching Method. Experimental Group students achieve high Performance of Speaking Skills in English because Integrated Life Situational Teaching enhancing their Speaking Skills in English.

Conclusion

Students enhanced their Speaking Skills in English through Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method. In Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method, students easily and interestingly involve Teaching-Learning Process. Integrating Life Situational Teaching Method gives meaningful Learning experiences to the students. In this method, the students and teacher actively participate and acquire Listening Skills in English.

Reference

- [1] Aslam Mohammed. (2003), The teaching of English, A practical Course for B.Ed Students published by Foundation Books, Daryaganj, New Delhi.
- [2] Baruah T.C. (1985), The English Teacher's Handbook. New Delhi: Sterling Publishing Pvt. Ltd.
- [3] Best, John W. (1977), Research in Education, Englewood Cliffs New Jersey: Prentice-Hall
- [4] Harris P.David. (1988), Testing English as a Second Language, TATA, MC Graw Hill publishing company Ltd 1974. Hayward, C.A - Alemanypren, Pergamon Press Ltd., Oxford, England.
- [5] Kholi A.L. (2000), Techniques of Teaching English in the New Millennium, DhanpatRai publishing company. New Delhi.

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ASSESSMENT OF ASANA PRACTICE AND NEUROMUSCULAR DRILLS ON ENDURANCE POWER OF SCHOOL LEVEL FENCERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the assessment of asana practice and neuromuscular drills on endurance power of school level fencers. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty fencing players with the age of 11 to 14 years from Fencing Coaching centre, Kanyakumari, Tamilnadu were selected as subject at random. The chosen subjects were divided into four equal groups namely experimental group one, two, three and control group. The experimental group-1 underwent asana practice (n=10, AP), experimental group-2 underwent asana practice combined with neuromuscular training (n=10, AP-NMD) and group-3 served as control group (n=10, CG), they did not participate any specific training. The selected treatment groups were performed their respective activities three days in a week, for the period of twelve weeks. The collected pre and post test data was critically analyzed descriptive statistics. To test the hypotheses 0.05 level of significance was used. The results of the present study demonstrated that the experimental groups produced significant alteration on endurance power than the control group.

Keywords: *Asana Practice, Neuromuscular Drills, Endurance Power, Ancova*

Introduction

The body in asanas is the vehicle for the development of wisdom, of spiritual awakening, and as such the body is held to be sacred and mastery of our body is considered the foundation for spiritual progress. In yoga we learn a discipline of the body which comes out of awareness and attentiveness, tuning in to our body's subtle energy flows and the life-giving rhythm of our breathing. The idea is that through entering more deeply and subtly into our physical experience, we can become more connected with ourselves, more grounded, and less swayed by anxieties or neurotic cravings for things that will not truly satisfy us. This can be a very positive influence on our approach to life, offering an antidote to the alienated rushing and disconnection from ourselves that characterizes much of our modern world. Marked evidence shows that neuromuscular drills programs are assessmentive for improving measures of performance. The benefits of a program designed for performance enhancement often include increased power, agility, and speed. Comprehensive neuromuscular drills programs designed for young women may significantly increase power, strength, and neuromuscular control and decrease gender differences in these measures Dynamic neuromuscular drills has also been demonstrated to reduce gender-related differences in force absorption, active joint stabilization, muscle imbalances, and functional biomechanics while increasing strength of structural tissues (bones, ligaments, and tendons).

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty fencing players with the age of 11 to 14 years from Fencing Coaching centre, Kanyakumari, Tamilnadu were selected as subject at random. The chosen subjects were divided into three equal groups namely experimental group one, two and control group. The experimental group-1 underwent asana practice (n=10, AP), experimental group-2 underwent asana practice combined with neuromuscular training (n=10, AP-NMD) and group-3 served as control group (n=10, CG), they did not participate any specific training. The selected treatment groups were performed their respective activities three days in a week, for the period of twelve weeks.

Table-I: The Results of Analysis of Covariance on Endurance Power of Selected Groups
(Scores in Minutes)

Test Conditions		AP	AP-NMD	CG	SV	SS	Df	MS	'F' Ratio	P value
Pre test	Mean	24.05	24.03	24.02	B	0.004	3	0.001	0.006	0.99
	S.D.	0.49	0.45	0.45	W	12.67	56	0.22		
Post test	Mean	23.81	23.50	24.2	B	9.23	3	2.92	29.47*	0.00

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	S.D.	0.43	0.17	0.44	W	5.8	56	0.07		
Adjusted post test	Mean	23.81	23.51	24.2	B	9.25	3	3.08	42.22*	0.00
					W	4.02	55	0.03		
*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The required table value for test the significance was 2.77 with the degrees of freedom 3 and 56, 3 and 55.										

Results on Upper Body Strength

The pre test mean and standard deviation on endurance power scores of G1, G2, and G3 were 24.05+0.49, 24.03+0.45 and 24.02+0.45 respectively. The obtained pre test F value of 0.006 was lesser than the required table F value 2.77. Hence the pre test means value of asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group on endurance power before start of the respective treatments were found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 56. Thus this analysis confirmed that the random assignment of subjects into four groups were successful. The post test mean and standard deviation on endurance power scores of G1, G2, and G3 were 23.81+0.43, 23.50+0.17, and 24.2+0.44 respectively. The obtained post test F value of 29.47 was greater than the required table F value of 2.77. Hence the post test means value of asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group on endurance power was found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 56. The results proved that asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group were produced significant alteration rather than the control group of the sample populations. The adjusted post test means on Endurance Power scores of G1, G2, and G3 were 23.81, 23.51 and 24.2 respectively. The obtained adjusted post test F value of 42.22 was higher than the required table F value of 2.77. Hence the adjusted post test means value of asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group on endurance power was found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 3 and 55. The results confirm that asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group on endurance power were produced significant difference among the groups. In order to find out the superiority assessments among the treatment and control groups the Scheffe's post hoc test were administered. The outcomes of the same are presented in the table I (a).

Table – I (A) Scheffe's Post Hoc Test Mean Differences among Three Groups on Endurance Power (Scores in Numbers)

AP	AP-NMD	CG	Mean Differences	CI Value
23.81	23.51	----	0.3*	0.25
23.81	----	----	0.68*	
23.81	----	24.2	0.38*	
----	23.51	----	0.37*	
----	23.51	24.2	0.69*	
----	----	24.2	1.1*	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

Result of Scheffe's post hoc test on upper body strength

Table I (a) shows the paired mean differences of asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group on upper body strength. The pair wise comparisons results as follows: The pair wise comparison between asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group, asana practice, asana practice combined with neuromuscular training and control group was 0.3, 0.68, 0.38, 0.37, 0.69, 1.1 respectively. These mean difference values were higher than the confidential interval value of 0.25. Hence, all the comparisons were significant. Therefore the training groups produced significantly different assessment on upper body strength. The adjusted post test mean difference of experimental and control group values on endurance power graphically represented in figure-1.

Discussion on Findings

The twelve weeks of training interventions have produced significant alterations on endurance power. The improvement of endurance power of experimental and control groups were discussed below: The asana practice assessment from pre (24.05 ± 0.49) to post (23.81 ± 0.43) has changed. The asana practice combined with neuromuscular training assessment from pre (24.03 ± 0.45) to post (23.50 ± 0.17) has changed. The percentage of improvement for asana practice and asana practice combined with neuromuscular training on endurance power was 0.99%, 2.20% and 3.74% respectively. The present study findings support in line with the results of the following earlier studies. The study findings from the assessment of asana practice on lower body power, physical fitness, and metabolic syndrome risk factors in school level fencing players demonstrated that the body weight, % body fat, and body mass index in the asana practice group was significantly decreased compared to the control group.

Conclusion

After the twelve weeks of training interventions, the experimental groups demonstrated significant alteration on upper body strength. The asana practice combined with neuromuscular training produced greater alteration on endurance power than the other training interventions. The least alteration was noticed in asana practice than the control group. The control group did not show any significant alterations.

References

- [1] Buddy Lee (2010). Jump rope training Champaign IL, Human Kinetics.
- [2] Chun-De Liao, Jau-Yih Tsauo, Li-Fong Lin, Shih-Wei Huang, Jan-Wen Ku, Lin-Chuan Chou, and Tsan-Hon Liou (2017). "Assessments of elastic resistance exercise on upper body strength and physical capacity in older women with sarcopenic obesity" *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2017 Jun; 96(23): e7115.
- [3] Debbie Lawrence, Richard (Bob) Hope (2015). The Complete Guide to Circuit Training. A&C Black Publisher.
- [4] Kim, Ko, Seo, (2018). "Assessment of asana practice on lower body power, physical fitness, and metabolic syndrome risk factors in obese female college students" *J Exerc Rehabil*. 2018 Jun 30;14(3):460-465. doi: 10.12965/jer.1836194.097. eCollection 2018 Jun.

IMPROVING MORAL EDUCATION FOR ADOLESCENT HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present article emphasizes that improving moral education for adolescent higher secondary school students. The moral education is most important for adolescent students who wants become a good citizen in the nation. Due to advancement of technology, the moral values and education level of the students is going down. Hence, the stakeholders take necessary steps to improve the moral values among the adolescent's students through providing moral classes and training to know the value of moral values in society. The development of society depends on the value of people who live in society. The people live in the society to learn many things from moral values of the society. Moral education of school students is of particular importance due to intensive development of information and communication technologies. The network resource fosters aggressive propaganda of ideas related to the culture of consumption, expression of violence, permissiveness, and promotes various forms of destructive behavior. The article highlights here improving moral education among adolescent higher secondary school students.

Key words: *Improving, Moral Education, Adolescents, Higher Secondary School Students.*

Introduction

School students need moral bearings to survive in the contradictory modern world and in the global information space. School teachers face difficulties with moral education of teenagers due to devaluation of moral values, destruction of the system of out-of-class and out-of school moral education that was strongly developed in the 1950-1980s of the 20 century, change of the sources of influence on younger generation (Gorelikov, 2018; Rachkovskaya, 2017). Today mass media and the Internet in particular, which is not limited to entertainment and communication, and quite often transmits stereotypes of immoral behavior, play a major role in the consciousness of the younger generation. Besides, the Internet and information and communication technologies contain considerable opportunities for the introduction of school student to universal moral values and new knowledge (Knyaginina, Meshkov, & Utolin, 2016; Proletarsky & Neusypin, 2014). This determines the problem of using extensive opportunities of the Internet in moral education of teenagers, as well as the need to develop their critical thinking and conscious attitude to received information.

Moral values –A glance

Moral values are standards that help an individual choose between good and bad. With a fair amount of morality being subjective, moral values tend to find their meaning open to interpretation in the general scheme of things. Ethical Values, in all their structure, are more of an absolute set of dos and don'ts that are distinguished by the social or community settings. The understanding of both is necessary to make honest, credible, and fair decisions and relations in daily life. Moral and ethical development is an essential process that should start from early childhood. Children can shape a good character and a pleasant personality by following moral values. The child's family plays a crucial role in guiding, supporting, and hand-holding them.

Importance of Moral Development

Moral development can be defined as the process that helps adolescents form a progressive sense of what is right and wrong, proper and improper (Dorough, 2011). Indian culture and philosophy has depicted varied instances in the scriptural texts where moral and value constructs have been used akin to psychotherapeutic constructs for dealing with emotions and for development of a human being (Bhide *et al.*, 2021). In the Bhagavad Gita (a sacred Hindu text), Lord Krishna helps resolve Arjuna's (the warrior) mental conflicts and moral dilemmas through the process akin to a psychological intervention (Bhatia *et al.*, 2013). Karma and reincarnation are two concepts from the Upanishads that allow one to become self-aware (improving one's personality). In terms of emotions, the Rig Veda acknowledges both positive and negative emotions (coping). The Yajur Veda shows the importance of self-esteem and self-worth and allows one to be in a space where he or she is able to be creative,

engaged, and happy. A 10-day residential yoga-based personality development program for adolescents in India has shown significant improvements in their emotional intelligence, emotional regulation and anger management, and self-efficacy, fine motor coordination, cognition, and personality (Choukse *et al.*, 2018; Das *et al.*, 2016; Patil & Nagendra, 2014).

Benefits of Teaching Moral Values to Children

- 1) Helps build a positive character with traits such as compassion, respect, kindness, and humility.
- 2) Makes the child distinguish between right and wrong or good and bad. It can eventually promote rational thinking and unbiased judgment.
- 3) Provides a perspective that shapes attitudes and beliefs towards various aspects of life.
- 4) Boosts their self-confidence and helps them stay positive even in difficult situations.
- 5) Allows children to channel their energies in the right direction.
- 6) Works as a moral compass that helps them stay off the negative influence of peers, social media, or society in general, as they grow into teens or adults.
- 7) Aids in setting high standards of social living that help develop society at large.

Improving Moral Education

Among academic disciplines and the world of action, every research project should act as an interpreter. Our obligation cannot be exhausted by academic task of establishing a proper conceptual analysis and then getting 'some result'. In the practice of moral education action and inaction are the two phases, it is presumed that in few circles in action is more welcome than inaction, as in inaction there will be less scope. For condemnation than inaction. The traditional concept of moral education is not the same as present day concept of moral education. Breakdown in authority, delinquency, the concrete phenomenon of crime are some of moral education's contents. But sophisticated conception involved many complex situations in rearing of child, the teacher and student relationship, atmosphere of school, the religious and moral bent of mind of the child and parental attitude to the child etc. The prime need of the present day is the development of moral skill rather than not breaking law of being disobedient to school teachers or parents.

Conclusion

This article concludes that improving Moral education in school adolescent students pays attention to the mold of overlooks on the world, life and values. It aims to cultivate students' ideology and morality and enlighten students' ideological and political consciousness, so that their physical and mental development can be comprehensive and healthy.

References

- [1] Knyaginina, V. N., Meshkov, N. A., & Utolin, K. V. (2016). Advanced education in the information society. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(3), 89-99.
- [2] Proletarsky, A. V., & Neusypin, K. A. (2014). Features of the use of modern information technology in education. *European Social Science Journal*, (1-1), 40.
- [3] Woodard, H. C., Shepherd, S. S., Crain-Dorough, M., & Richardson, M. D. (2011). The globalization of higher education through the lens of technology and accountability. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(2), 16-24

SKILL BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM MEET FUTURE DEMAND OF WORKFORCE

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Abstract

With an age range of 15-59 years, India is among the world's young generation countries, with students and working class both included. India has a great opportunity to meet the future demands of the world. India is becoming the fastest hub worldwide for sourcing skilled students and workers. The Indian economy is ruled by innovation and knowledge in a world of tremendous opportunities and risks, facing complex business, political, scientific, technological, health, and environmental challenges. The importance of generic and specific skills, a global perspective of skills gaps and reasons for these skills gaps, and how the Indian education system fulfils the request for skill development and meets the challenges Knowledge and skills are developed in training programmes; apprenticeship programmes are also not like formal schooling. Skill building can be viewed as an instrument to improve the effectiveness and contribution of labour to overall production. These are determined targets that prove the need for significant change. It is extremely difficult, but not impossible, for an education system to respond to these challenges quickly and in the right ways—particularly in a country as large and diverse as India. The education system is struggling to address significant issues around basic skills. This is the first time that the Indian economy requires a workforce, an education system, and specific educational skills.

Key Words: *Skill Learning, Education System, Entrepreneurship, Vocational Training*

Introduction

Whether hiring required only degrees to be consider or skilled manpower can be hired is always a question. The effect of pandemic COVID-19 when there was potential recession, still rising inflation rates and highest attrition rates have driven employers to rethink their approach to human resource management and talent management. The skills needed to meet the growing demand for caring professions and the skills needed by an aging workforce will likely be affected by demographic change. Trends in education have been equally dramatic. Throughout human history most people were not formally educated. In today's society, many young people are unemployed, despite the fact that they attend school and earn degrees that can help them in their careers. This unemployment is caused by a variety of factors, including shifts in the types of jobs needed to support the economy and changes in the economy. Organizations and the private sector are attempting to provide solutions to the problem of youth unemployment. They are using robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), and other cognitive solutions to improve, customer satisfaction, value and improve service and quality. There are three key elements any organisation: work (what gets done), workforce (by whom or what), and workplace (where and how). Organizations must re-evaluate the work being done and ensure they are focused on work that creates value for the organisation. Along with traditional employees, the modern workforce era frequently includes contingent workers like contractors, freelancers, and gig workers. Also, it's possible that the modern workforce is not entirely human. As a result, 200 new nursing assistants underwent this clinical training.[1] The World Economic Forum predicts that 50 percent of all employees will need to reskill by 2025 to respond to advances in technology.[2] By removing degree requirements from job postings or expanding sourcing pools, employers could get started on implementing skills-based practices sooner. However, they ought to monitor a long-term strategy: When skills-based practices are implemented throughout the entire talent journey, including sourcing, hiring, and career development, their impact is maximized. "India's job landscape is in transition with a slowdown in employment in core sectors and the concurrent emergence of new engines of job creation. Over the next few years, many other factors such as the levels of FDI flow, impact of exponential technologies on off-shoring, increase/decrease in overseas job opportunities for the Indian labour force, speed of adoption of emerging technologies, demands resulting from environmental sustainability, rising middle class and a high proportion of young population, would be some of the other key determinants of future of jobs in 2022.[3] Given the constant and accelerating pace of change, skills development strategies will be obliged to ensure the continual renewal of skills over the life cycle. This will require focusing on ways to manage the different transitions that individuals will face (for example, moving from the informal to the formal economy or from the manufacturing to the services sector), so that they successfully enter the labour market. [4]

Methodology

This paper will discuss some of the important skill-based education-related approaches and evidence in the education system through systematic reviews of literature, Primary sources, related articles, and other materials. The questionnaire was prepared and circulated among 4 companies staff members. The questionnaire was having 20 closed ended and open ended questions. Total 175 full response was received and results are discussed.

Results

95% participants in the survey were having degree in art, science or any other stream as their highest education qualification. Many organisations don't have robust man force, structure in place for regular hiring process. In addition, recent college graduates, a traditionally dependable source of talent, frequently lack the required competency level for key skills, as stated by 87% of the participants. 85% of the participants indicated that skills-based career postings resulted in a considerable increase in applications from a larger set of workers. Skilled based practices provide a read map for workers to make advancements, allow employees process and slower hiring process. Few participants also reply that they are more satisfied with the job given on the base of their skills then on the degree. Hiring for skills is five times more productive in job performance than hiring for education and more than two time more predictive than hiring for work experience. 95% of the participant respond on that workers without degree and having skills tend to stay in their jobs 35 percent longer than workers with degrees. 80% of the participant response that they will move to the new roles where their skills will be more utilised then organisations where less skill and require more training. Employers should create skills based pathways for all manpower at certain time interval so that skills can be polished and can move from lower level to higher level positions as and when available. It is difficult to bridge the gap between workers' existing skills and the skills they need to grow. Even though many workers who started in origin roles have strong foundational skills like customer service, they still need training to learn the skills specific to their job, and there is no quick way to teach those skills to workers. Employers were unsure of how to communicate the opportunities available at their organizations to these workers and which jobs, particularly lower-paying positions held by many workers without degrees, could produce the best candidates. Although they were confident in their ability to eliminate degree requirements, they lacked confidence in the appropriate and efficient methods they used to validate a candidate's proficiency in particular skills through assessments or interview questions. Implementing skills-based practices beyond immediate HR professionals can be challenging, along with skills validation and sourcing: Recruiters and HR personnel frequently support skills-based hiring, but hiring managers may need more convincing.

Conclusion

Skills-based employment creates a more robust workforce and can be an effective strategy for employers to prevent attrition, which is especially relevant in the present era. By defining the required skills rather than the preferred competencies, changing the norms to stop using credentials as a proxy for skills, and connecting with community organizations that provide workforce support to reach potential candidates, employers can first create a robust skills framework for all positions. Employers anticipate that critical thinking and analysis, problem-solving, and self- management skills like active learning, resilience, stress tolerance, and adaptability will be among the most sought-after skill sets in the year 2025. Companies have recognized that skills-based hiring are a powerful solution to challenges that have intensified. Through a skills-based approach, organizations can boost the numbers of manpower and quality of work. Employers are assisting workers to find and providing opportunities to internal staff which is also helping in employee retention rate. It also helps communities by creating better job opportunities, diverse pool of manpower in any the organization.

References

- [1] Taking a skills-based approach to building the future workforce. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/people-and-organizational-performance/our-insights/taking-a-skills-based-approach-to-building-the-future-workforce>. Accessed on 01-01-2023.
- [2] Kate Whiting, "These are the top 10 job skills of tomorrow – and how long it takes to learn them," World Economic Forum, October 21, 2020.
- [3] Baishali Mukherjee. "Why Skill-based Learning Is Vital In Today's Job Market Reality". January 2, 2019. Blog – Career Guidance.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

VARIOUS PROBLEMS FACED BY STUDENT – TEACHERS IN THE RURAL AREAS IN KERALA DURING COVID

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Abstract

The paper focuses on the various problems faced by student-teachers in the rural areas in Kerala during Covid. The main problems were the isolation process during covid, the lack of mingling with peers, lack of proper internet connectivity for attending online classes, financial problems, anxiety about course and future job opportunities, lack of co-curricular activities, lack of technical knowledge, availability of gadgets, unemployment of family members, family problems, social problems, health problems etc. Here, this paper concentrate on the various problems faced by student-teachers especially in the rural areas in Kerala during Covid pandemic situation

Keywords: *Various Problems, Rural Areas, Covid*

Introduction

Any pandemic is worst, especially one like Covid, during the Covid situation for student-teachers in the rural areas in Kerala there will be so many problems in their mind. They will be concerned over the future of the course and also if they get good job opportunities in the future at the same time, they will be concerned over there health and other related issues.

Isolation

We have to separate ourself from other is known as isolation. As covid is a pandemic condition, we all have to isolate ourself from others in order to dodge from this virus. This may last for at least 7 days to 15 days. This will affect mentally. We cannot mingle with others directly which may cause serious traumas that may require psychological counselling.

Lack of Mingling

Man is a social animal, during covid we cannot mingle with others because of strict rules and protocols. This also causes psychological problems which may last for a long time. As an individual, society has a special affect on us. Without proper mingling with peers and others one cannot survive.

Network Problems

Network problem is a main issue, nowadays not only for rural areas but also for urban areas. At the time of covid, work from home for IT employees and online classes for students caused a lot of connection problems. The usage of Internet has been increased dreadfully. This caused Internet access problems especially in rural areas where the number of network towers are not so large.

Financial Problems

Finance is the backbone of every human being. We cannot survive without finance. During Covid a lot of people lost their job especially private jobs. Business persons also suffered huge loss because they cannot open the shop to sell the products. This pandemic caused financial problems which will affect any person directly or indirectly. So all were worried about the future and health but financial problems will affect our mental health adversely.

About Course and Job

B.Ed is a professional course, everyone will get job after completing the course. But when covid arises the student teachers have worried about the future of the course because it needs physical presence of student-teachers in the class room for practical works like micro teaching, internship, etc. so they have been worried about the course. And also they were worried about the future job opportunities for them because they have been termed as 'online batch' which may adversely affect their future job opportunities.

Lack of Co-Curricular Activities

Lack of Co-Curricular Activities will cause mental and physical trauma to all especially for student-teachers as they were mentally stressed out with lot of worries and worries about their course. If we participate in more such activities, our health condition as well as psychological conditions will become better. It will make us better human beings.

Lack of Technical Knowledge

Technical Knowledge is a very modern language which is essential now a days. But in rural areas the use of technology is very low. So they were not aware of latest technology and other things. This will adversely affects student-teacher participation in online classes which requires google meet or zoom and google class room applications. Without proper technical knowledge, we cannot survive in this modern era. It is a irreplaceable thing in this era. Better technical knowledge will make us better to survive in this competitive world. Unavailability of Modern Gadgets. The unavailability of modern gadgets is a big issue in rural areas.

Unemployment

During Covid a lot of people become unemployed. So the main financial income of the family gets disturbed in most cases. So unemployment causes financial insecurity to the family which will affects student – teachervery badly. All professions especially teaching profession had affected the COVID very adversely. Lot of institutions cut short their number of employees and payment had been decreased. These all will have a negative impact among student - teachers.

Family Problems

Family is the back bone of every human being. Due to the pandemic, we can't able to mingle with our family or even with our elderly father, mother, grandparents and with our small kids freely due to the fear of getting infected. So at this time, as there are lot of struggle for student - teachers regarding their course, they also have many family problems. We can't seperate ourselves from our family. We can't survive without the support from our family and this makes things even worst. If students especially student - teachers doesn't have family support, the issue is bigger. So family problems will affect student - teachers very badly.

Health Problems

One of the main issues prevailed during COVID was health issues. It is the basic and most important thing for a human being. Health is wealth. During COVID, health issues taken a toll on student - teachers body and mind. They were weak, but at the same time they have to maintain a good health by taking good food. But financially they will not be at their best at that time, so they have to balance the health by taking good food and thinking positive things and doing some exercrise especially breathing exercises. Positive thinking is the main thing we have to do at that time inorder to be mentally fit and healthy.

Conclusion

Covid is a severe pandemic which affected the whole world. It affected student-teachers also, they become worried about the course and job opportunities. In Rural areas, there were lot of problems apart from urban areas. This paper discusses such problems that arises in rural areas in Kerala among student – teachers during covid. In Kerala, there were lot of educational institutions. So there is lot more scope of employment for student - teachers. But due to COVID, all these circumstances has changed. Teachers had been terminated from the jobs and also have a cut short in wages. All these problems created a big concern over the future of student - teachers.

Reference

- [1] Jena, Pravat Kumar, Impact of Covid-19 on Higher Education in India (2020).
- [2] Pokhrel S, & Chhetri R (2021), A Literature Review on Impact of covid-19 pandemic on teaching and learning.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

A STUDY ON STUDY SKILLS AND CONTENT PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE OF B.ED. BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article focuses its attention on the study skills and content pedagogical knowledge of B.Ed. Biological Science Students. For this, the investigator adopted survey method of research. The population comprises of all the B.Ed. biological science students studying in the colleges of education in Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Kanyakumari districts. From the population, the investigator randomly selected 619 students using simple random sampling technique. Self-constructed Study Skills Inventory and Self-constructed Content Pedagogical Knowledge Scale were used as the tools of the study. Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' test and Product Moment Correlation were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that significant relationship is found between study skills and content pedagogical knowledge of B.Ed. biological science students.

Keywords: *Study Skills, Content Pedagogical Knowledge, Biological Science Students.*

Introduction

Education plays a vital role in the determination of the career of every individual. Since the destiny of a nation is being shaped in the classroom, the teacher holds the entire responsibility by instilling certain skills and required mastery over the subject knowledge in the minds of the younger generation through making the classroom learning more meaningful one. Among all the skills, the study skills have been played an important role in the determination of academic performance of the students. The study skills are helpful for the learner to learn the concept efficiently. Generally, The study skills of a learner revealed the innate capabilities of the learner not only in the classroom but also in their overall academic excellence. Moreover, the teacher has to know the subject matter in an elaborate manner and he or she has able to know how to teach those content in an efficient way to the best of understanding of the learner. Despite a teacher's deep understanding of a subject area he or she must also be able to foster understanding of subject or concepts for students.

Study Skills

Any skill that increases a student's ability to learn, keeps and restores information, which helps to pass the examination, can be termed as a 'Study Skill'. In other words, study skills are the skills, which are required to enable the learners to learn efficiently (Bremer, Rod, 2016). These skills are an important set of transferable life skills. Study skills include time management and motivational methods. They are individual skills that can be learnt in a shorter period of interval. They can be differentiated from various other skills, and from intrinsic abilities like intelligence level and learning style of the students. These skills are series of skills, which tackle the process of organizing and taking in new information, retaining the same information or dealing with measurement of the same information. They include mnemonics that helps the retention of series of information; effective reading of those information; concentration techniques and note taking (Bruner, J., 1974). Regarding the students' point of view, study skills are inevitable that is, without good study skills, the students cannot be able to learn the subject matter which in turn, they are not able to perform well in their examinations. Hence, it is more and more important to analyse the factor - study skills of the chosen sample.

Content Pedagogical Knowledge

Content Pedagogical Knowledge is the overlap of information about subject knowledge being taught, and pedagogic knowledge, that is knowledge of how to teach. Despite a teacher's deep understanding of a subject area he or she must also be able to foster understanding of subject or concepts for students. Shulman (1987) identified "content pedagogical knowledge" as the most useful forms of representation of the ideas of the teacher that is conveyed to the taught with the most powerful analogies, illustrations, examples, explanations, and demonstrations, the ways of representing the subject that make it comprehensible to others. It also includes an understanding of what makes the learning of specific topics easy or difficult: the conceptions and preconceptions that students of different ages and backgrounds bring with them to learning. (Joyce, B. and Weil, M. 2000).

Content pedagogical knowledge also includes conceptual and procedural knowledge, a repertoire of varied techniques or activities (which meet different learning styles) knowledge of techniques for assessing and evaluating, and knowledge of a variety of resources, which can be easily accessed for use in the classroom (Farah J. Farooqi, 2006). Hence, the future teachers should be capable of having this to enrich their competency to teach the subject matter in an efficient manner.

Need and Significance of the Study

The quality of teacher education depends upon the quality, efficiency and competency of teacher educators. The teachers should be expertized in certain skills like controlling their self, thinking capacity, problem solving and the like. The future teachers should be highly motivated to learn new concepts and techniques, and acquire various skills in order to improve their proficiency in teaching that are helpful to the nation building process. All the school going children require certain skills and have to practise them to successfully develop their knowledge database. These skills play a vital role in deciding their levels of achievement, which may decide their career. The ambitions and aspirations of the students are largely governed by their skills. Moreover, above all the skills, the student teachers should be capable of handling different students with different capabilities under different critical situations. With the broad spectrum of cognitive characteristics, there may be strengths and weaknesses, which influence their study skills and their pedagogical content pedagogical knowledge of student teachers. Hence, the investigator would like to take up this study.

Title of the Study

A STUDY ON STUDY SKILLS AND CONTENT PEDAGOGICAL KNOWLEDGE OF B.Ed. BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE STUDENTS

Definition of the Key Terms

Study Skills

Study skills refer to one's ability or competence to learn and master the subjects. By this term, the investigator means study methods employed in general, in the classroom, in doing homework, in preparing for the examination and overcoming the obstacles of effective study.

Content Pedagogical Knowledge

Content pedagogical knowledge refers to a type of knowledge that is unique to teachers, and is based on the manner in which the teachers relate their pedagogical knowledge (what they know about teaching) to their subject knowledge (what they know about what they teach).

B.Ed. Biological Science Students

By 'B.Ed. Biological Science Students', the investigator means the student teachers studying two years B.Ed. degree course having the optional subject - biological science.

Objectives

- 1) To find the level of study skills and content pedagogical knowledge of B.Ed. biological science students.
- 2) To find the significant difference in the study skills of B.Ed. biological science students with regard to certain background variables - gender, family type and locality of residence.
- 3) To find the significant difference in the content pedagogical knowledge of B.Ed. biological science students with regard to certain background variables - gender, family type and locality of residence.
- 4) To find the significant relationship between study skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students and their content pedagogical knowledge.

Method and Procedure

The investigator adopted survey method. The population comprises of all the B.Ed. biological science students studying in the colleges of education in Tirunelveli, Thoothukudi and Kanyakumari districts. From the population, the investigator randomly selected 619 students using simple random sampling technique. Self-constructed Study Skills Inventory and Self-constructed Content Pedagogical Knowledge Scale were used as the tools of the study. Mean, Standard Deviation, 't' test and Product Moment Correlation were used to analyze the

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data.

Analysis and Findings

Percentage Analysis

Level of Study Skills and Content Pedagogical Knowledge of B.Ed. Biological Science Students.

Table 1 Level of Study Skills and Content Pedagogical Knowledge of B.Ed. Biological Science Students

Dimensions	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Study Method	31	5.00	486	78.50	102	16.50
Classroom Skills	50	8.10	452	73.00	117	18.90
Home work	60	9.70	336	54.30	223	36.00
Examination	41	6.60	425	68.70	153	24.70
Obstacles to Effective Study	78	12.60	435	70.30	106	17.10
Study Skills in Total	36	5.80	486	78.50	97	15.70
Content Pedagogical Knowledge	118	19.10	387	62.50	114	18.40

From the above table, it is inferred that 5.80% of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students have low, 78.50% of them have moderate and 15.70% of them have high level study skills in total. 5.00% of them have low, 78.50% of them have moderate and 16.50% of them have high level study method. 8.10% of them have low, 73.00% of them have moderate and 18.90% of them have high level classroom skills. 8.10% of them have low, 73.00% of them have moderate and 18.90% of them have high level home work skills. 6.60% of them have low, 68.70% of them have moderate and 24.70% of them have high level examination skills. 12.60% of them have low, 70.30% of them have moderate and 17.10% of them have high level obstacles to effective study. It is also inferred that 19.10% of the students have low, 62.50% of them have moderate and 18.40% of them have high level content pedagogical knowledge.

Null Hypothesis - 1

There is no significant difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to gender.

Table - 2 : Difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Gender

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Study Method	Male	44	51.80	4.840	1.133	NS
	Female	575	52.65	4.814		
Classroom Skills	Male	44	6.55	.975	0.198	NS
	Female	575	6.57	.915		
Home work	Male	44	5.09	.709	1.669	NS
	Female	575	5.26	.654		
Examination	Male	44	12.89	1.482	1.367	NS
	Female	575	13.24	1.657		
Obstacles to Effective Study	Male	44	7.45	1.405	0.294	NS
	Female	575	7.53	1.546		
Study Skills in Total	Male	44	83.77	7.976	1.194	NS
	Female	575	85.25	7.897		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table, that the calculated 't' values are less than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted in the case of study skills in total and in all the dimensions. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the male and female students in their study skills in total and in all the dimensions.

Null Hypothesis - 2

There is no significant difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to

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family type.

Table - 3 : Difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Family Type

DIMENSIONS	Family type	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Study Method	Nuclear	261	53.02	4.805	1.905	NS
	Joint	358	52.27	4.808		
Classroom Skills	Nuclear	261	6.65	.995	1.752	NS
	Joint	358	6.52	.856		
Home work	Nuclear	261	5.31	.744	1.937	NS
	Joint	358	5.21	.586		
Examination	Nuclear	261	13.51	1.645	3.855	S
	Joint	358	13.00	1.617		
Obstacles to Effective Study	Nuclear	261	7.23	1.718	3.972	S
	Joint	358	7.73	1.349		
Study Skills in Total	Nuclear	261	85.71	7.881	1.531	NS
	Joint	358	84.73	7.908		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table, that the calculated 't' value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected in the case of study skills related to examination and Obstacles to Effective Study. Therefore, it is concluded that there is significant difference between the students belonging to nuclear and joint families in the study skills related to examination and obstacles in effective study. The students belonging to nuclear families have better study skills related to examination and obstacles in effective study than their counterparts in joint families. It is also inferred from the above table, that the calculated 't' values are less than the table value at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the students belonging to nuclear and joint families in the study skills in total and in the dimensions - study method, classroom skills and homework.

Null Hypothesis – 3

There is no significant difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to locality of residence.

Table 4 : Difference in the Study Skills of B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Locality of Residence

DIMENSIONS	Locality of Residence	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Study Method	Rural	521	52.64	4.865	0.631	NS
	Urban	98	52.31	4.569		
Classroom Skills	Rural	521	6.59	.918	0.844	NS
	Urban	98	6.50	.922		
Home work	Rural	521	5.26	.649	0.424	NS
	Urban	98	5.22	.711		
Examination	Rural	521	13.21	1.666	0.074	NS
	Urban	98	13.22	1.550		
Obstacles to Effective Study	Rural	521	7.53	1.539	0.500	NS
	Urban	98	7.45	1.520		
Study Skills in Total	Rural	521	85.23	8.045	0.600	NS
	Urban	98	84.70	7.140		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table, that the calculated 't' values are less than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the rural and urban students in their study skills.

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Null Hypothesis - 4

There is no significant difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to gender.

Table - 5 : Difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Male	44	103.98	18.333	1.064	NS
Female	575	100.32	22.232		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value is less than the table value at 5% level of significance. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the male and female students in the content pedagogical knowledge.

Null Hypothesis - 5

There is no significant difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to family type.

Table - 6 : Difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Family Type

Family Type	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Nuclear	261	94.15	22.782	6.285	S
Joint	358	105.26	20.162		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between the students belonging to nuclear and joint families in their content pedagogical knowledge. The students belonging to joint families have better content pedagogical knowledge.

Null Hypothesis - 6

There is no significant difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to locality of residence.

Table - 7 : Difference in the Content Pedagogical Knowledge of the B.Ed. Biological Science Students with respect to Locality of Residence

Locality of Residence	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Rural	521	101.45	22.039	2.357	S
Urban	98	95.92	21.203		

(At 5% level of significance the table 't' value is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance.

Null Hypothesis - 7

There is no significant relationship between study skills and content pedagogical knowledge of B.Ed. biological science students.

Table - 8 : Relationship between Study Skills and Content Pedagogical Knowledge of B.Ed. Biological Science Students

Dimensions	N	Calculated 'r' Value	Remark
Study Method	619	0.276	S
Classroom Skills	619	0.164	S
Home work	619	0.251	S

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Examination	619	0.345	S
Obstacles to Effective Study	619	0.098	S
Study Skills in Total	619	0.263	S

(Table Value = 0.095 at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'r' value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

The researcher concluded that the B.Ed. biological science students have moderate level of study skills and content pedagogical knowledge. Their gender does not have any significant influence on their study skills and content pedagogical knowledge. The family type has significant influence on their study skills and content pedagogical knowledge. The finding of the correlation analysis revealed that significant relationship is found between the study skills of B.Ed. biological science students and their content pedagogical knowledge. From these observations, it is obvious that study skills and content pedagogical knowledge are the vital factors in the process of teaching and learning more effectively. Hence, the liability of the teacher communities is to consider these factors that should be instilled in the minds of younger generation for making a brighter tomorrow.

References

- [1] Bremer, Rod. 2016. The Manual: A Guide to the Ultimate Study Method (2nd ed.). CA: Fons Sapientiae Publishing.
- [2] Bruner, J. 1974. Toward a Theory of Instruction. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- [3] John W. Best and James V. Kahn. 1992. Research in Education, 6th Edition. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
- [4] Joyce, B. and Weil, M. 2000. Models of Teaching. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.\

DIVERSITY IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Today Indian education has come a long way with a much higher number of children getting access to education. Correspondingly, there has been increasing number of learners from diverse backgrounds entering the classrooms. It is a phenomenon that is rapidly manifesting in the present day. Everyone who comes to the classroom is unique having special attributes, and personality traits. The individual differences that we notice in each child may be attributed to his/her cultural, social, economic, and political background. We need to understand these differences in order to embrace diversity. Diversity needs to be expected, respected, and celebrated. The classroom is an ideal platform to engage young students in discussions regarding diversity and in still values such as tolerance, acceptance empathy and compassion. Such efforts will make them future ready with the right knowledge, skills, competencies, and attitudes to participate fully in the processes of social, economic, and political development in the present day. The teacher has tremendous responsibility to recognize and accommodate all of these in the classroom. Students on their part are uncertain whether they would be accepted or if they will 'fit in' the class.

Keywords: *Diversity and Education.*

Introduction

The word diversity is derived from the French word 'diversite' which means 'making dissimilar'. According to Webster's Dictionary, 'Diversity is the condition of having or being composed of different elements especially the inclusion of different types of people or organization. So, when the word diversity is used in social context, it indicates a group of people or individuals who are different from each other in some way or the other. It also implies collective differences among people, those differences which distinguishes one group from another. These differences may be related to culture, language, gender, religion, physical appearance social and economic status, family structure, abilities, values, and beliefs. If viewed from the perspective of uniformity, diversity is the antonym of uniformity. Whereas uniformity is derived from 'Uni' and 'form' that is one form, or similar, diversity means variety. At the educational level, diversity is an umbrella term that refers to students who are different from one another. It means the understanding that each student is unique and recognizing that individual differences exist among students. Diversity is valuing such differences among students and the ways in which these differences can contribute to making learning environment in classrooms more vibrant, rich and productive. It also implies that we acknowledge that differences cannot be categorized into watertight compartments, nor are they fixed. It is celebrating individual differences and celebrating the varied dimensions of diversity in each learner. It is a way to explore and incorporate these differences which would lead to enriched learning. From such explanations it becomes clear that diversity as a concept encompasses acceptance and respect for all students. It promotes equity, equality and inclusiveness in the education institutions.

Nature of Diversity

There is an astounding variety in virtually every aspect of Indian society. Diversity with respect to cultural, linguistic, regional, economic, religious, class gender, and caste groups, have permeated even to the classrooms. Teachers encounter a diverse set of students. Some differences may be obvious like physical appearances, accent, and gender. However, some may not be so visible outwardly like religion, socio-economic background. Moreover, students also come from different racial, ethnic, and linguistic backgrounds. They may have different learning styles, different levels of motivation and different opinions about the world around them. Their ideas, perspectives, and values may also differ. All such characteristics make one individual or group different from another. As mentioned earlier, apart the race, ethnicity, and gender innumerable factors, like age, national origin, religion, disability, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, education, marital status, language, physical appearance, level of motivation, learning styles, etc. also contribute to classroom diversity.

Types of Diversity

- 1) Cultural Diversity
- 2) Race
- 3) Ethnicity

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- 4) Gender
- 5) Social Class
- 6) Economic Diversity
- 7) Disability
- 8) Religion
- 9) Linguistic Diversity

In the field of education, it can be illustrated by, citing examples of measures taken by certain schools and colleges to augment their online teaching mode. A school may provide tablets for all students to facilitate online classes. But some students may not have internet facilities at home, or they may not be comfortable using tablets. There might be problem of coping with new methods of learning. Schools may treat them as equal by providing same gadgets, but progress and achievement of using the resources would vary to a great extent. The measures are based on the principle of equality but not equity as individual needs are not considered. By ensuring equity in classroom, we can reap many benefits for students and for society as well. Some of the major advantages are:

- 1) Enhancing the quality of classroom environment;
- 2) Understanding student's individual challenges and offering tailored support;
- 3) Opportunity for every child to try and succeed;
- 4) Improving academic achievement;
- 5) Increasing cooperation and collaboration among students;
- 6) Improving mental health conditions, direct correlation with socio emotional quotient;
- 7) Improving physical health and life span; and
- 8) Contributing to economic growth.

Strategies to Address Classroom Diversity Are:

- 1) Recognizing the increasing Diversity of classrooms:
- 2) Differentiated Instruction.
- 3) Interactive pedagogy.
- 4) Scaffolding.
- 5) Cooperative collaborative learning.
- 6) Accepting different perspectives.
- 7) Tap into students' backgrounds.
- 8) Holistic approach.
- 9) Teacher Capacity Building.
- 10) Equitable participation.
- 11) Capitalize on multiple intelligences.

Conclusion

The national policies may reiterate that equality and equity with respect to access and outcomes are highly essential for quality of the education system and reaching the Sustainable Developmental Goals. Quality is not confined to improving the quality of school infrastructure or improved access to education. Diversity is much more than just teaching or preaching, it is also about practicing in classrooms. Quality is reflected in the various ways by which the diverse learners are nurtured to maximize their potential. All stakeholders must be encouraged to take collective responsibility to dispel stereotypes that are major hindrances in accepting diversity. The new NEP 2020 has taken cognizance of this need by laying stress on demystifying such stereotype.

References

- [1] Anderson, K.M. (2007). Differentiating instruction to include all students: preventing school failure. *Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 51(3), 49-54.
- [2] Berne, E. (1961). *Transactional analysis in psychotherapy*. New York: Grove Press.
- [3] Betancourt, H., and Lopez, S. R. (1993). The Study of culture, ethnicity, and race in American Psychology. *American Psychologist*, 48(6), 629- 637.
- [4] Brualdi, A. (1998). Multiple intelligences: Gardner's theory. *Teacher Librarian*, 26 (2), 26-29.
- [5] Government of India.(2020). *National Education Policy 2020*.
- [6] Kothari Commission (1964- 1966),

GENDER TRAUMA IN MAYA ANGELOU'S "I KNOW WHY THE CAGED BIRD SINGS"

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Experiences shared by Black people worldwide by virtue of their common denominator-Blackness or their radicalized community-is termed as racism. Racist behavior often results in racial discrimination, with its obvious negative consequences, ranging from simple neglect, avoidance of those believed to be different and inferior or more explicit forms of harassment, exploitation or exclusion. The Great Depression of the 1930s worsened the already bleak economic situation of African Americans. They were the first to be laid off from their jobs, and they suffered from an unemployment rate two to three times that of whites. In early public assistance programs African Americans often received substantially less aid than whites, and some charitable organizations even excluded blacks from their soup kitchens.

The word 'race' emerged in the English language in 1508 in the poem 'The Dance of the Seven Deadly Sins by the Scotsman', William Dunbar. Though there were substantial literature in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries about Africans and other non-Europeans, the word 'race' was rarely used either to describe peoples or in account of differences between them and it was largely took part in the Southern lifestyle during the 1930's. Even the segregation prevailed in buses, schools and also in parks.

Researchers have found that discrimination in general, and racial discrimination in particular, deteriorates mental health of individuals. Angelou accepts her blackness as a positive attribute for responding racists in a very optimistic manner and adopts her black colour as her identity rather than cursing it.

In this autobiography, Maya Angelou expressed realistically about her own life without omitting incidents and added certain essence of fiction to awake from the racial discrimination in the society and to recreate the African-American identity. The life of Maya Angelou depicts the survival of African American people in the racially discriminated society. Being an African American, she became a great role model for her survival against difficult situations in her life. Maya Angelou tells the story of her childhood: a childhood full of hardships and calamities, but also filled with the beauty and innocence of childhood. She tells the story of her rushed childhood, in a world that did not give her the chance or the time to live a proper one.

James Olney says, "Black history was preserved in autobiographies rather than in standard histories" (Autobiography.15). The autobiography mainly reflects the contemporary times of an individual and conveys the hindrance in the way of the author's self-development, resistant and the uncountable success he/she achieved. Maya Angelou's autobiographies are a series of transformations her works also reflects the struggles for survival in an oppressive world. This struggles in Maya Angelou's life made an inner spark/urge to write about her own life. The racial discrimination and the identity to survive is the main sequence of struggle in Maya Angelou's autobiography I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings. Being a marginalized child, the socially constructed notion troubles Maya and her childhood development.

Maya's parents divorced when she was only three years old and ship Maya and her older brother, Bailey, to live with their paternal grandmother, Annie Henderson, in rural Stamps, Arkansas. They travelled through train with a porter and they noticed a big difference between desegregation in California and the segregated South. Maya's skewed perception came because fellow black passengers took pity on the children and shared their meals. They did not receive the same courtesy from white passengers, who were less likely to pack large meals.

Maya narrates,

I don't remember much of the trip, but after we reached the segregated southern part of the journey, things must have improved. Negro passengers, who always travelled with full lunch boxes, felt sorry for "the poor little motherless darlings" and gave us lots of cold fried chicken and potato salad.(CB.5)

Despite the warmth of her new home, Marguerite felt abandoned by her parents and throughout all her childhood she felt so, but fortunately, she had a lovely brother and friend who was the only person who could understand her feeling. She loved him so much and he was the essence of her life as she described him -"Bailey was the greatest person in my world. And the fact that he was my brother, my only brother and I had no sisters to share with him, was such good fortune that it made me want to live a Christian life just to show God I was grateful" (CB.22).

Annie, whom they call Momma, runs the only store in the black section of Stamps and becomes the central moral figure in Maya's childhood. As young children, Maya and Bailey struggle with the pain of having been rejected and abandoned by their parents. A successful business woman and a religious fundamentalist, Momma was a strict disciplinarian who taught Maya and Bailey values and respect. In little Maya's eyes, Momma

was very sturdy and powerful.

I saw only her power and strength. She was taller than any woman in my personal world, and her hands were so large they could span my head from ear to ear. Her voice was soft only because she chose to keep it so. In church, when she was called upon to sing, she seemed to pull out plugs from behind her jaws and the huge, almost rough sound would pour over the listeners and throb in the air. (CB.47)

Momma seems to be a typical image of black women, who is big and strong with large hands and loud voice. Being cared for and protected by such a Momma, Maya had a sense of security. Momma told Maya about the harshness of slavery and how the Africans were taken from their land to the United States, but she still encouraged Maya to believe that freedom would come one day. Throughout her life, Momma served as a positive influence on Maya. Even the indomitable grandmother, Anne Henderson, rises each morning with the consciousness of a caged animal. She prays, "Guide my feet this day along the straight and narrow, and help me to put a bridle on my tongue" (CB.7). But, it is from her that Marguerite begins to learn how to survive in the cage. She updates the Bible passages to their reality. She said that as freedom had come to Moses and the Jewish people, so black people's day of freedom would come. It was only a matter of time:

Momma added that some people said that white folks had come over to Africa (she made it sound like a hidden valley on the moon) and stole the coloured people and made them slaves, but nobody really believed it was true. No way to explain what happened "blows and scores" ago, but right now they had the upper hand. Their time wasn't long, though. Didn't Moses lead the children of Israel out of the bloody hands of Pharaoh and into the Promised Land? Didn't the Lord protect the Hebrew children in the fiery furnace and didn't my Lord deliver Daniel? We only had to wait on the Lord. (CB.196)

In Stamps, the custom was to 'can' everything that could possibly be preserved. During the killing season, after the first frost, all neighbors helped each other to slaughter hogs and even the quiet, big-eyed cows if they had stopped giving milk. Throughout the year, until the next frost, we took our meals from the smokehouse, the little garden that lay cousin-close to the Store and from the shelves of canned foods. There were choices on the shelves that could set a hungry child's mouth to watering. But at least twice a year Momma would feel that as children we should have fresh meat included in our diets.

Maya and Bailey occasionally accompany their grandmother in her shop, which she owned for some twenty-five years. There they came to know about the mistreatment of the white people towards the African people. There were boundaries in place to keep black and white communities separated. In Stamps the separation was so complete that most black children did not really, absolutely know that what Whites looked like. Other than that they were different, to be dreaded and in that dread was included the hostility of the powerless against the powerful, the poor against the rich, the worker against the worked for and ragged against the well dresses (CB.25).

Additionally, Maya was told stories about violence against black people at the hands of the whites that add to Maya's fear of the unknown. At many courses, Mrs. Henderson was disrespected by the white people as Mrs. Henderson was a very strong spiritual person she never felt being insulted by them. Hilary Crew stated that, "the voice of the grandmother is strong, as she disciplines and protects her granddaughter in the racial inequality" (Crew.86)

In an act of resistance, Momma refused to subscribe to the local newspaper, *The Democrat*, because as she said, "It is written by white folks, about white folks, for white folks" (CB.51). Instead, she supported newspapers that provided greater racial representation, in spite of those papers being published in northern cities and not arriving immediately.

She was beautiful. Something had happened out there, which I couldn't completely understand, but I could see that she was happy. Then she bent down and touched me as mothers of the church "lay hands on the sick and afflicted" and I quieted. "Go wash your face, Sister". And she went behind the candy counter and hummed, "Glory, glory, hallelujah, when I lay my burden down". I threw well water on my face and used the weekday handkerchief to blow my nose. Whatever the contest had been out front, I knew Momma had won. (CB.33)

This scene is a dramatic, symbolic recreation of the kind of spiritual death and regeneration Angelou experienced during the shaping of her development. But it is also a vivid recapturing of Black/White tensions in the South of the 1930s. On the one hand, three white girls, attempting to use their race as an overbearing instrument of power, treat a Black woman like another child, practicing the rituals of white power with the full sanction of the white community and attempting to reduce the Black woman to their level. On the other hand, the Black woman chooses the dignified course of silent endurance.

Although Mrs. Henderson knows that she must accord the girls some modicum of respect, she refuses to recognise them as anything but white children, refuses to register their offensiveness or humanity, refuses to play their game. Seeking to preserve her own integrity and to transcend the ugliness of their actions, Mrs. Henderson

wins a psychological victory by using this weapon to transcend the limitations of her social world. White dominance intrudes on other occasions that also teach Maya vital lessons in courage and survival and open her eyes to the fact that she belongs to an oppressed class. The old saying “an eye for an eye” does not apply to this woman because to forgive and forget are more important. Even though Maya thinks that her grandmother is weak at times, it could be observed that what Momma does is to create survival strategies.

Another example of racism is demonstrated when a politician speaks at her eighth-grade graduation. Maya explains how her graduation day excited everyone in the town. Even though she was graduating from the eighth grade, her family felt much excited. Maya tells us “The children in Stamps trembled visibly with anticipation” (CB.169). Maya herself is excited and admits that she didn't expect to survive until graduation. Her brother, Bailey, gives her a leather-bound copy of Edgar Allen Poe's poetry and her grandmother cooks a breakfast normally reserved for Sunday. But the happiness was short lived as the Black students at Maya's school are disheartened when at class eighth graduation ceremony the White chief guest demoralizes the Black students with his racist speech.

Maya feels that he has blemished the joy of the graduation day by insinuating that black children only achieved greatness through sports, not through academics. The members of the eighth-grade class hang their heads in shame. Maya laments the fact that she has no control over her life and wishes that Christopher Columbus never sailed to the New World. After his speech, Donleavy rushes to leave. Then there is a reaction from a member of the Black community; Henry Reed's spontaneous response leads the Black audience in singing:

Lift ev'ry voice and sing
Till earth and heaven ring
Ring with the harmonies of Liberty.(CB.182)

The song is labelled as Black National Anthem' and every African American present in the hall sings it. In the same futile response against the White girls, the song evades an out-and-out clash with the White tormenter and consents the Black people to feel its pride and supremacy: “We were on top again. As always, again. We survived. The depths had been icy and dark, but now a bright sun spoke to our souls”. (CB.184)

It was not the reason that the black people faced their consequences because of their own voluntary activities or arrangements, but it was the unfortunate circumstances that they were forced to faced the circumstance of racial discrimination. It was evident through Maya Angelou's one of the bitter experience of her graduation day.

Against the backdrop of racial tensions in the South, Angelou confronts the traumatic events of her own childhood and explores the evolution of her own strong identity as an African American woman. Her individual and cultural feelings of displacement are mediated through her passion for literature, which proves both healing and empowering. Maya writes, “During these years in Stamps, I met and fell in love with William Shakespeare. He was my first white love”(CB.13). Maya writes that,

“But it was Shakespeare who said, When in disgrace with fortune and men's eyes. It was a state with which I felt myself most familiar. I pacified myself about his whiteness by saying that after all he had been dead so long that it couldn't matter to anyone any more”.(CB.14)

Angelou accepted her traumatic life and with that experience she proved to be a successful person among the African-American people and became their role model.

Reference

- [1] Angelou, Maya. *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*. Random, New York, 1969. Print.
- [2] Bernanke, Ben. The Macroeconomics of the Great Depression: A Comparative Approach. *Journal of Money, Credit, and Banking*, Blackwell Publishing, 27(1),1995, pp. 1-28.
- [3] Paul A. Brown, *Annual Bibliography*, Vol. 77, No. 2, May, 1961, pp. 171.
- [4] Vandergrift, Kay E. And Bid Her Sing: A White Feminist Reads African-American Female Poets. *SCILS* 14, November, 2005, pp.123.
- [5] Olney. *Autobiography and the cultural Moment*.*Autobiography:Essays Theoretical and Critical*. Princeton UP, New Jersey,1980, pp. 3- 27.
- [6] Hilary S Crew. *Feminist theories and the voices of mothers and daughters in selected African-American literature for young adults*, Scarecrow Press,1998, pp.86.

EFFECTIVENESS OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON FEMALE DIABETICS PATIENTS

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Abstract

The study was to find out the effectiveness of yogic exercises on female diabetics patients from the Dindigul District, 40 female diabetics were chosen for this study. They had already received medical care, and their ages ranged from 40 to 55. The patients are divided into equal groups for the experimental and control conditions. The experimental group participated in an eight-week yoga programme, while the control group received only their standard medical care. The dependent variable is determined to be blood glucose levels. If there is a significant difference between groups, the t-test is employed to determine it. Following an eight-week training period, it was found that the yoga Practitioners Achieved Greater Results than the Controls.

Keywords: *Yoga, Diabetes*

Introduction

The Excessive blood glucose levels are a hallmark of the metabolic diseases known as diabetes mellitus (hyperglycaemia). Problems with insulin action, secretion, or both may be to blame for this. Beta cells in the pancreas islets of Langerhans produce the hormone insulin. The anti-insulin hormone glucagon is produced by alpha cells. Both collaborate to keep the blood's level of glucose constant. Blood glucose can enter body cells through insulin, providing them with energy and fuel for work. Insulin also acts as a gatekeeper. While an excess of glucose remains in the circulation, diabetes impairs cellular fuel.

Methodology

The aim of the study was Find out how yogic exercises effectiveness of yogic practices on female diabetic patients. forty female diabetic patients from the Dindigul district were selected to work toward this goal. Ages 40 to 55 were represented by them. The two groups of diabetes patients experimental and control were divided equally. In addition to their usual medical care, the experimental group participated in eight weeks of yoga. Regular medical care was provided to the control group. Plasma glucose levels were measured in both the experimental and control groups before and after the eight-week period. The t-test was used to find the difference between the groups, with 0.05 being the level of significance.

Training Programme

The experimental groups went through their separate training programmes during the training period. The duration of each training session was around forty five minutes, which included warming up and limbering down. To avoid injuries, all subjects in this study were closely monitored during the training regimen. Throughout the training programme, they were asked about their health. They reported no injuries or inconvenience. Muscle soreness, on the other hand, emerged early in the workout programme and gradually subsided.

Training Details of Yogic Practice

Duration of the training : 8 weeks
Number of days per week : 5/3 Days
Duration of the session : 45 Minutes

Table – I computation of t-ratio between pre and post test of experimental and control group

Variable	Group	Pre mean	Post mean	S.D Pre	S.D Post	T test
Glucose	Control Group	360.00	349.50	84.57	55.05	1.12
	Experimental Group	361.50	295.00	57.33	34.25	8.32*

*Significant at 0.05 level

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From the above table it was clearly shown the difference in plasma glucose for experimental group 8.32* is higher than the table value of 2.09. At the same time there is no difference in control group 1.12 at the level 0.05 level of significance.

Figure-I Mean Difference between Pre and Post test of Experimental and Control Group

Discussion on Finding

The findings of the study show that the experimental group significantly improved in the dependent variable. At the same time, it demonstrates that there is no substantial difference in the control group. Malhotra, et al (2005) examined at the end of the 40 days of performing the asanas, on average the study participants had a decrease in fasting glucose levels, a significant decrease in waist-hip ratio and beneficial changes in insulin levels.

Conclusion

It was determined that the blood glucose was lowered as a result of twelve weeks of yoga practises. It was concluded that there was significant difference between experimental group when compare the control group .

References

- [1] Malhotra V, Singh S, Tandon OP, Madhu SV, Prasad A, Sharma SB (2002), Effect of Yoga asanas on nerve conduction in type 2 diabetes, *Indian Journal of Physiology & Pharmacology*, Jul;46(3):298-306.
- [2] Kyizom T, Singh S, Singh KP, Tandon OP, Kumar R (2010), Effect of Pranayama & Yoga asana on cognitive brain functions in type 2 diabetes-P3 event related evoked potential (ERP), *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, May; 131:636-40.
- [3] Kosuri M, Sridhar GR (2009), Yoga practice in diabetes improves physical and psychological outcomes, *Metabolic Syndrome and Related Disorders*, Dec;7(6):515-7.
- [4] AljasirBadr, Maggie Bryson and Bandar Al-shehri (2010), Yoga Practice for the Management of Type II Diabetes Mellitus in Adults; A systematic review,” of the University of Ottawa, *Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, Volume 7 Issues 4, Pages 399-408.
- [5] Amita S, Prabhakar S, Manoj I, Harminder S, Pavan T (2009), Effect of yoga-nidra on blood glucose level in diabetic patients, *Indian Journal of Physiology & Pharmacology*, Jan Mar;53(1):97-101.
- [6] V.Preethi,Dr.S.Saroja.(2022), “Yoga in the Management of diabetics” *International Journal of Advance and Applied Research*, Aug ;Volume 9 Issues 6, p.p 187-189

MENTAL HEALTH AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THANJAVUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

Mental health is a level of psychological well-being, or an absence of mental illness. It is the psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioural adjustment. Achievement is one's actual abilities which can be measured directly by the use of tests. Achievements are sometimes best measured in the field of practical situation. Educational achievement test show how much knowledge and skill an individual has obtained (and trained) in a school subject such as arithmetic, science, history or geology. It is reported that Mental Health has a significant decrement onto students' achievement. This study aimed to determine the association between Mental Health and Academic Achievement of higher secondary school students in a Thanjavur District. Survey method of research was used. A sample of 210 students was selected from different higher secondary schools of Thanjavur District through Simple Random sampling technique. The self developed Mental Health and Academic Achievement questionnaire was used to collect the data. The result of the research is that there is no significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Gender, Locality and Types of Institution. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Subject. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

Keywords: *Mental Health, Academic Achievement, Higher Secondary School Students*

Introduction

Mental health is a level of psychological well-being, or an absence of mental illness. It is the "psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioral adjustment". From the perspective of positive psychology or holism, mental health may include an individual's ability to enjoy life, and create a balance between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mental health includes "subjective well-being, perceived self-edifice, autonomy, competence, inter-generational dependence, and self-actualization of one's intellectual and emotional potential, among others. "The WHO further states that the well-being of an individual is encompassed in the realization of their abilities, coping with normal stresses of life, productive work and contribution to their community. Cultural differences, subjective assessments, and competing professional theories all affect how 'mental health' is defined. A widely accepted definition of health by mental health specialists is psychoanalyst Sigmund Freud's definition, the capacity "to work and to love". Achievement is one's actual abilities which can be measured directly by the use of tests. Achievements are sometimes best measured in the field of practical situation. Educational achievement test show how much knowledge and skill an individual has obtained (and trained) in a school subject such as arithmetic, science, history or geology. The world is becoming more and more competitive quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. Parents desire that their children climb the ladder of performance to as high a level as possible. This desire for a high level of achievement puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, schools, and in general, the educational system itself. In fact, it appears as if the whole system of education revolves round the academic achievement of students, though various other outcomes are also expected from the system. Thus a lot of time and effort of the schools are used for helping students to achieve better in their scholastic.

Need and Significance of the Study

Mental health is universally agreed upon by all people who are concerned with social welfare and progress of a country that the teacher plays a crucial role in building of nation and truly the teacher is called National builder. Teaching has become increasingly challenging and complete ends these present changing conditions. One of the various challenges hurled at teachers recent part, is of maintaining the physical and mental health of children and youth of nation. It is a new responsibility of Teacher. Teachers can play an important role in maintain the vertical health of the nation with their knowledge of human problems and remedial measures. For

health pupils, the teacher takes about the mental health of the pupils. Academic achievement may be called as academic performance or learning outcomes of the students. It is a factor to show the student's internal consistency and capability of memory. Academic achievement as independent and dependent variables respectively.

Review of Related Literature

The investigator reviewed the following research studies. Joshi (2000) conducted a study on neuroticism, extraversion and academic achievement as related to gender and culture. The sample selected for the study was 400 students of eight classes belonging to urban and rural area of Punjab. School records and Eysenck's personality inventory was used for data collection. Results revealed a significant difference between boys and girls of rural areas on academic achievement. Devi and Brian (2002) studied factors related to scholastic backwardness of secondary school children. 100 low achievers from secondary school of Hyderabad city were selected as sample for the study. Interview schedule was used to elicit factors related to scholastics of parents found to be detrimental to academic achievement of their children. Nalwa and Anand (2005) highlighted the negative impact of Mental Health on Students Academic Achievement. The present study is intended to study the impact of Mental Health on the Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. Jan et al (2006) conducted a study to investigate whether juvenile delinquents use lower levels of moral judgment than their nondelinquent age-mates and results show a lower stage of moral judgment for juvenile delinquents. Moral judgment is strongly related to academic achievement. Park and Choi (2007) found that Boys students use more Mental Health than Girls students. There are a number of studies on the Mental Health among Boys and Girls students. Despite the gender equality and constitutional safeguards for the Girls, the Boys dominated the Mental Health in Secondary School Students. Pardhasardhi and Goel (2015) studied the influence of access to use of Mental Health on Academic Achievement of adolescents. The data was analyzed using method of descriptive statistics and the finding revealed that the Mental Health was useful for education and it had a positive influence on students Academic Achievement. Mir and Paray (2018) studied the Mental Health and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students in Kashmir. The study found significant difference between the Academic Achievement scores of Mental Health user and non-users students, where the Mental Health users performed well in academic score as compared to the non-users.

Statement of the Problem

A problem must spring from the researcher's mind like a plant springing from its own seed. To the same point of view, in education, most of the researches have been conducted in different ways and angles among the development of student's academic achievement through the teacher's factors and the classroom factors. These factors contribute their equal influence to successful teaching and learning process. If there is any unbalanced effect on participation of those factors which leads to a negative effect on the educational outcomes. Although, no researcher can identify the exact unbalanced contributing factor to make an indirect effect on learning outcomes. It is not possible to find the interior contribution of a factor on the same. Because each factor has several contributions of those factors. For this backdrop, the investigator of the study has interested to conduct a study on mental health and academic achievement. Here the study is entitled "A Study on Mental Health and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students of Thanjavur District".

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find the level of Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- 2) To study the difference in Mental Health in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 3) To study the difference in Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 4) To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students

Hypothesis of the Study

- 1) There is no significant difference in Mental Health in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 2) There is no significant difference in Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.

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- 3) There is significant relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.

Methodology of the study

The Normative survey method is adopted for the study. The variables used are the Mental Health and Academic Achievement. Population: Higher Secondary School Students in Thanjavur District are the population of this study. Sample: The sample consists of 210 higher secondary school students from both Government and Matriculation school in Thanjavur District. Tools: Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school student's questionnaire was used. The inventory contains 20 & 18 objective items. This was a self developed tool. Validity and reliability of the tool: The sample reliability is established by test-retest method by the investigator and the reliability co-efficient is found to be 0.73. Hence the tools are highly reliable. The validity of the test was assessed on the basis of the judgment of the experts. Procedure of data collection: The Mental Health and Academic Achievement Questionnaire will be given to the selected sample with a request to fill in the required data enclosing a copy of permission letter from the school Head Master.

Data Analysis

Table-I: Mean and SD of variable Mental Health and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Mental Health	210	14.84	5.86
Boys	107	12.11	4.63
Girls	103	13.01	4.75
Rural	102	12.35	3.90
Urban	108	13.40	4.76
Arts	104	12.42	3.94
Science	106	13.76	4.45
Government School	101	13.30	4.67
Matriculation School	109	12.85	3.23

Table-II: Mean and SD of variable Academic Achievement and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Academic Achievement	210	12.81	4.53
Boys	107	11.66	3.20
Girls	103	11.85	3.30
Rural	102	11.54	3.51
Urban	108	12.13	3.86
Arts	104	11.66	3.16
Science	106	12.10	3.91
Government School	101	12.11	3.95
Matriculation School	109	11.86	3.02

Table-III: Mean, SD and 't' value of Mental Health and its sub-variables

Variable	Values			t	S
	No.	Mean	SD		
Boys	107	14.84	5.86	1.55	NS
Girls	103	12.11	4.63		
Rural	102	13.01	4.75	1.60	NS
Urban	108	12.35	3.90		
Arts	104	13.40	4.76	1.98	S
Science	106	12.42	3.94		
Government School	101	13.76	4.45	1.73	NS
Matriculation School	109	13.30	4.67		

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Table-IV: Mean, SD and 't' value of Academic Achievement and its sub-variables

Variable	Values			t	s
	No.	Mean	SD		
Boys	107	12.81	4.53	1.63	NS
Girls	103	11.66	3.20		
Rural	102	11.85	3.30	1.72	NS
Urban	108	11.54	3.51		
Arts	104	12.13	3.86	2.16	S
Science	106	11.66	3.16		
Government School	101	12.10	3.91	1.80	NS
Matriculation School	109	12.11	3.95		

Table-V Correlation Analysis

Variable	Values		
	No.	'r'	S
Mental Health and Academic Achievement	210	0.130	S
Boys	107	0.119	S
Girls	103	0.103	S
Rural	102	0.135	S
Urban	108	0.116	S
Arts	104	0.011	NS
Science	106	0.022	NS
Government School	101	0.113	S
Matriculation School	109	0.109	S

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

Mental Health

- 1) The level of Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students is high.
- 2) Mean score of Girls is higher than the Boys on Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- 3) Mean score of urban school students Mental Health is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students.
- 4) The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Mental Health.
- 5) The students studying in government higher secondary school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Mental Health.

Academic Achievement

- 1) The level of Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students is high.
- 2) Mean score of Girls Academic Achievement is higher than the Boys in higher secondary school students.
- 3) Mean score of urban school students Academic Achievement is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students.
- 4) The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Academic Achievement.
- 5) The students studying in government school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation school with respect to Academic Achievement.

Differential Analysis

Mental Health

- 1) There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- 2) There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- 3) There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- 4) There is no significant difference between Government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.

Academic Achievement

- 1) There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- 2) There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- 3) There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- 4) There is no significant difference between government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.

Correlation Analysis

- 1) There is a significant relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students. Also there exists significance relationship among Boys, Girls, Rural, Urban, Government and Matriculation School.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students with respect to Arts and Science.

Suggestions for the Further Research

- 1) This study can be extended to high school students.
- 2) This study is limited only to the selected higher secondary school students in Thanjavur District only and it to be extended to all types of schools and colleges.
- 3) The present study was carried out during the short period of time with limited samples.
- 4) The findings and conclusion are needed to be verified larger group size of the samples.

Conclusion

The result of the research is that there is no significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Gender, Locality and Types of Institutions. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Subject. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

References

- [1] Basumalik, T. and Bhattacharya, K.P. 1980. Views of Mental Health. Third Survey of Research in Education, New Delhi. NCERT.
- [2] Nathawat, S.S. 1977. A Study of Creativity in Relation to Mental Health, Ph.D Psy. Kerala University.
- [3] Pandey, A.K. and Pandey, R.K. 1998. A Study of Mental Health and Decision-Making Capacity of Higher Secondary School Principals. Praachi, Journal of Psycho-Cultural Dimension, 2(9-11).

CONSENSUAL OUTCOME OF THERAPEUTIC YOGA ASANAS ON BODY MASS INDEX AMONG CLASS I OBESE

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of therapeutic yoga asanas on body mass index among class I obese men. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty class I obese were selected from Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India during the year 2022. The subject's age ranges from 20 to 25 years. The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups consists of 15 subjects each namely experimental group and control group. The experimental group underwent a therapeutic yoga asanas programme for eight weeks. The control group was not taking part in any training during the course of the study. BMI was taken as criterion variable in this study. The selected subjects were tested on Body mass index was measured through body mass index analyzer method. Pre-test was taken before the training period and post- test was measured immediately after the six week training period. Statistical technique 't' ratio was used to analyse the means of the pre-test and post test data of experimental group and control group. The results revealed that there was a significant difference found on the criterion variable. The difference is found due to therapeutic yoga asanas given to the experimental group on Body mass index when compared to control group.

Keywords: *Therapeutic, Yoga Asanas, BMI*

Introduction

Yoga is fundamentally connected with the prosperity of human body. In spite of the fact that it is said that the last point of yoga is to accomplish Moksha or Nirvana, a few yogic practices are instrumental in keeping up great wellbeing. Today, sports have become a part and parcel of our culture. It is being influenced and does influence all our social institutions including education, economics, arts, politics, law, mass communication and even international diplomacy. Yoga is universally benefiting all people of all ages. The study of Yoga is fascinating to those with a philosophical mind and is defined as the silencing of the mind's activities which lead to complete realization of the intrinsic nature of the Supreme Being. In the sports world, physical education is the most essential aspect due to the fact physical schooling increases the performance and the effectiveness of the sports.

Research Methodology

Selection of subjects: The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of therapeutic yoga asanas on Body mass index among class I obese men. To achieve this purpose of the study, thirty class I obese men were selected as subjects at random. The age of the subjects were ranged from 20 to 25 years. **Selection of variable:** Independent variable: Therapeutic yoga asanas practice, Dependent variable: Body mass index. **Experimental Design and Implementation:** The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each, such as a therapeutic yoga asanas training group (Experimental Group) and control group. The experimental group underwent therapeutic yoga asana training for six days per week for eight weeks. Control group, which they did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical activities as per their curriculum. The Body mass index was selected as criterion variable. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected criterion variable Body mass index was measured through body mass index analyzer method at prior to and immediately after the training programme. **Statistical Technique:** The 't' test was used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively. **Level of Significance:** The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent 't' test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

Table I Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post tests of experimental and control group on Body mass index (Scores counts in number)

Variables	Group	Mean		SD		df	't' ratio
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post		
Body Mass Index	Control	32.20	32.16	1.14	0.92	14	0.32
	Experimental	32.40	30.92	1.29	1.95		9.01*

*Significance at .05 level of confidence.

The Table-I shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the control group on Body mass index were 32.20 and 32.16 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.32, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.14 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The obtained 't' ratio was 9.01* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.14 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant.

Figure-1 Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of Experimental and Control Group on Body mass index

Discussions on Findings

The result of the study indicates that the experimental group, namely therapeutic yoga asanastraining group had significantly improved the selected dependent variable, namely body mass index, when compared to the control group. It is also found that the improvement caused by therapeutic yoga asanas training when compared to the control group.

Conclusion

On the basis of the results obtained the following conclusions are drawn, There was a significant difference between experimental and control group on Body mass index after the training period. There was a significant improvement in Body mass index. However the improvement was in favor of experimental group due to eight weeks of therapeutic yoga asanastraining.

References

- [1] Marinar Rai., et.al, (2020). The power of yoga. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.6225-6229.
- [2] Sumitra Das., et.al, (2020). Consequence of yoga and rowing. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.7079-7084.
- [3] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Combination of naturopathy and yoga on VO2 max among hypertensive patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(04), pp.131-134.
- [4] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Effect of yoga therapy on BMI rate among class I obese patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(05), pp.143-146.

A PRECISE LEARNING ON MEDITATION PRACTICES ON MENTAL CONCENTRATION ABILITY

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of mindfulness meditation practices on concentration ability among school children. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty primary school children were selected from Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, India during the year 2022. The subject's age ranges from 20 to 25 years. The selected students were divided into two equal groups consists of 15 subjects each namely experimental group and control group. The experimental group underwent a mindfulness meditation programme for six weeks. The control group was not taking part in any training during the course of the study. Mental concentration ability was taken as criterion variable in this study. The selected subjects were tested on concentration ability was measured through concentration cognitive assessment (CAB-AT) questionnaire. Pre-test was taken before the training period and post- test was measured immediately after the six week training period. Statistical technique 't' ratio was used to analyse the means of the pre-test and post test data of experimental group and control group. The results revealed that there was a significant difference found on the criterion variable. The difference is found due to mindfulness mediation given to the experimental group on mental concentration ability when compared to control group.

Keywords: *Mindfulness Mediation, Mental Concentration, 'T' Ratio.*

Introduction

Mindfulness meditation is a mental training practice that teaches you to slow down racing thoughts, let go of negativity, and calm both your mind and body. It combines meditation with the practice of mindfulness, which can be defined as a mental state that involves being fully focused on "the now" so you can acknowledge and accept your thoughts, feelings, and sensations without judgment. "Concentration is the ability to direct one's attention in accordance with one's will. It means control of the attention. During concentration, the mind focuses on the object of concentration, and only one thought occupies the mind.

Research Methodology

Selection of Subjects: The purpose of the study was to find out the mindfulness meditation practices on concentration ability among school children. To achieve this purpose of the study, thirty primary school children were selected as subjects at random. The age of the subjects were ranged from 14 to 16 years. **Selection of variable:** Independent Variable: Mindfulness Meditation, Dependent Variable: Mental Concentration Ability. **Experimental Design and Implementation:** The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each, such as a mindfulness meditation group (Experimental Group) and control group. The experimental group underwent mindfulness meditation for six days per week for six weeks. Control group, which they did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical activities as per their curriculum. The following psychosocial variable namely mental concentration ability was selected as criterion variable. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected criterion variable Concentration ability was measured through concentration cognitive assessment (CAB-AT) questionnaire at prior to and immediately after the training programme. **Statistical Technique:** The 't' test was used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively. **Level of Significance:** The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent 't' test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

Table I Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post tests of experimental and control group on Concentration ability (Scores in numbers)

Variables	Group	Standard Deviation		Sd Error	
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Concentration ability	Control Group	0.63	0.48	0.16	0.12
	Experimental Group	0.63	0.45	0.16	0.11

Table II

Variables	Group	Mean		Degree of freedom	't' ratio
		Pre	Post		
Concentration ability	Control Group	5.60	5.66	14	0.435
	Experimental Group	5.53	3.73	14	16.83*

*Significance at .05 level of confidence.

The Table-I and II shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the control group on concentration ability were 5.60 and 5.66 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.435, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.14 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group on concentration ability were 5.53 and 3.73 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 16.83* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.14 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant.

Figure-1 Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of Experimental and Control Group on mental concentration Ability

Discussions on Findings

The result of the study indicates that the experimental group, namely mindfulness meditation group had significantly improved the selected dependent variable, namely concentration ability, when compared to the control group. It is also found that the improvement caused by mindfulness meditation when compared to the

control group.

Conclusion

On the basis of the results obtained the following conclusions are drawn, There was a significant difference between experimental and control group on concentration ability after the training period. There was a significant improvement in concentration ability. However the improvement was in favor of experimental group due to six weeks of mindfulness meditation.

Reference

- [1] Sumitra Das., et.al, (2020). Consequence of yoga and rowing. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.7079-7084.
- [2] Marinar Rai., et.al, (2020). The power of yoga. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.6225-6229.
- [3] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Combination of naturopathy and yoga on VO2 max among hypertensive patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(04), pp.131-134.
- [4] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Effect of yoga therapy on BMI rate among class I obese patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(05), pp.143-146.
- [5] James Rathinaraj, S., Yoga, P., Alaguraja, K., & Selvakumar, K.(2020). Combination of walking practices and yogic practices on low density lipoprotein (Ldl) among middle aged women. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(06), pp.362-365.
- [6] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2017). Influence of yogasana practice on flexibility among obese adolescent school boys. International Journal of Yoga Physiotherapy and Physical Education, 2(7), pp.70-71.
- [7] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2018). Effect of core stability training on dynamic strength among college male students. International Journal of Yogic Human Movement and Sports Sciences, 3(2), pp. 436-437.
- [8] Yoga, P., Balamuralikrishnan, R., & Alaguraja, K. (2018). Influence of cyclic meditation on selected physiological parameter. International Journal of Advanced Education and Research, 4(1), pp.17-18.
- [9] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2019). Effect of yogic practice on resting pulse rate among school students. Indian journal of Applied Research, 9(7), pp. 43-44.
- [10] Marinar Rai., Yoga, P., Alaguraja, K., Selvakumar, K., & Sumitra Das. (2020). The power of yoga. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.6225-6229.
- [11] Sumitra Das., Yoga, P., Alaguraja, K., Selvakumar, K., & Marinar Rai. (2020). Consequence of yoga and rowing. International journal of advanced science and technology, 29(03), pp.7079-7084.
- [12] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Combination of naturopathy and yoga on VO2 max among hypertensive patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(04), pp.131-134.
- [13] Alaguraja, K., & Yoga, P. (2020). Effect of yoga therapy on BMI rate among class I obese patient. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(05), pp.143-146.
- [14] James Rathinaraj, S., Yoga, P., Alaguraja, K., & Selvakumar, K.(2020). Combination of walking practices and yogic practices on low density lipoprotein(Ldl) among middle aged women. Indian journal of public health research & development, 11(06), pp.362-365.
- [15] Selvakumar, K., & Yoga, P. (2019). Influence of yogic practice on flexibility among college students, Indian journal of Applied Research, 9(7), pp. 45-46
- [16] Sumitra Das., & Yoga, P. (2019). Effect of yogic package on body mass index among rural school girls, Journal of Information and Computational Science, 9(8), pp.462-467.
- [17] Sumitra Das., & Yoga, P. (2019). A study on effect of combined yoga and naturopathy on triglycerides among high school girls, Journal of Information and Computational Science, 9(8), pp.450-454.
- [18] Yoga P. (2020). Scientific Technological Evaluation of Isolated and Companied Practices of Yogic Practices and Meditation on Psychological Conditions of College Students. International journal of scientific & technology research. 9(2). pp. 6257-6258.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

This research study made an attempt to examine the impact of technology on holistic education. Technology is such an integral part of our daily lives that it is impossible to consider education and teaching without including digital technology. The transition to e-learning has permanently altered education. Students and educators now expect to be able to access their learning environments at any time and from any location, and they are increasingly demanding access to modern, cloud-based technologies that allow them to work flexibly, reduce burdens, and achieve their full academic potential. To address these needs, educational institutions must take a holistic approach to education technology (EdTech), encompassing platforms for teaching and learning but also addressing long-standing challenges including student achievement, retention, accessibility, and educational integrity. It can be scary for many students who are embarking on this digital transformation journey and expecting to fully embrace EdTech. Though access and retention in education have significantly increased, the goal is to provide equitable, quality, lifelong learning, and comprehensive education that integrates 21st century skills as well as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In this research paper some the review of literature and information gather from secondary sources of data prepared this research paper. It has the power to reach out to every corner of the country and bridge the digital divide by providing teaching, learning, assessment, and continuing professional development solutions at any time and from any location, while also reaching size and speed.

Keywords: *Holistic Education, Technology, Digital Transformation, Edtech, Automation, Platform*

Introduction

The way we learn is changing as a result of technological advancements. Gone are the days when we had to learn information and then recite it in an exam. With the arrival of new technologies and devices, the education sector has undergone a sea change and been fundamentally revolutionized. The emphasis is shifting away from theory and rote learning and toward skill development and problem-solving abilities. Holistic education is a relatively recent approach that emerged in the 1980s to oppose the prevailing mechanistic learning system in the United States. The philosophy of educating based on a person's full experience has its origins in ancient concepts of instruction, such as those of Greek and other indigenous civilizations, and has grown in popularity over the last century. Several systems based on whole-person education gained traction in the twentieth century. Learning conditions, whole-child services, and social and emotional development are all measurable elements of education that can promote equality and outcomes, according to school systems. Even today, technology has permeated every element of life, and as technology evolves, so must an individual's abilities and knowledge. Innovative educational technology is a critical tool for engaging students, stimulating their curiosity, and improving their entire learning experience. It creates and promotes the possibility of delivering essential concepts to youngsters in a customised style that is simple for them to understand. People's opinions have become more polarised as a result of technological advancements. Ideas propagate at breakneck speed on social media sites, leading to radical stances and human conflicts. To avoid limiting viewpoints on issues, education must take a broad approach. Adopting technology in the classroom does not imply abandoning traditional approaches. In the event that technology fails, a mix of digitization and physical presence is the ideal remedy. In this manner, instructors will still have access to offline teaching resources and will be able to ensure that students' functioning and learning do not halt. Backup preparations with activities, as well as using this occasion to impress on pupils the necessity of adaptation and imaginative thinking, are excellent solutions to technological failure.

Research Gap

The digital divide must be addressed as a top priority, with equitable access to digital tools and learning opportunities provided for all students. A positive collaboration with parents will aid in closing this gap. Effective use of digital resources and hybrid learning methodologies will be an extra qualification for teachers. Emotional, social, physical, artistic, intellectual, and psychic developments are all part of education. Some of these areas may be jeopardised unless there is a one-on-one bonding session with students. Engaging classes may help to increase

motivation and engagement. Few therapies for differently abled pupils, such as occupational therapy, may be jeopardized unless they interact with the teacher in person.

Review of Literature

Rajita Kulkarni (2021), "Holistic Learning in Higher Education Institutions in India: A Sustainable Approach," according to which the researcher explained that the educational system in India and around the world is expanding rapidly in terms of providing students with multi-disciplinary possibilities to learn. Since the epidemic, e-learning platforms have grown at an exponential rate. Keeping up with the demands of Industry 5.0, the NEP-2020 aimed to "establish a model of education aimed not just on cognitive growth, but also on character development and generating holistic and well-rounded individuals armed with critical 21st century abilities." In the coming years, multi-country, multi-religion, and multi-language virtual workplaces will become more common. June Lee, Yong-Lyun Kim, and Eun Young Jang (2020), the author elaborated, "The purpose of this study is to theoretically analyse techniques for successful management of smart schools, in which technology is the primary factor driving change, not only in classroom instruction but also in school education as a whole." First, the writers investigate the shift in the educational paradigm that will assist society in the future, as well as the changes in the teaching and learning processes. Following that, the issues surrounding existing studies on technology utilisation and the breadth of technologies available in schools are examined. Third, a comprehensive plan for implementing smart school administration is proposed. The study finishes with a synopsis of the techniques required to develop and operate a smart school. Kaladevi, P. S. (2020), "Holistic Development of Education," as based on the researcher's concern The National Education Policy was established in 1968, and the regional language was employed in schools. Because education is a vital aspect of skill development, the Indian government has created an education policy system to help students enhance their knowledge. Prior to independence, India was dominated by the British. At the time, the Indian people were illiterate, and they had no idea what education was or how it worked. However, the British government eventually moved forward to provide education to Indians in order for them to know how to control a state if they could learn about the education system and strive to develop their talents. Sule Betül Tosuntaş, Zühal ubukçu, and Tubanci (2019), "A Holistic View to Barriers to Technology Integration in Education," according to which "technology integration" is a long-term and consistent transformation in the social system of schools brought about by the use of technology to help students construct knowledge. Although technology integration initiatives cannot have a single goal, studies are undertaken and application examples are developed to make the integration process more successful and efficient. Many studies are aimed at identifying and removing barriers to technology integration. Factors influencing technology integration in education are handled differently in the literature, and multiple categories are utilized. The purpose of this research is to gather the findings of previous studies on factors influencing technology integration in education. In other words, after removing external impediments to technological integration, instructors' knowledge, abilities, attitudes, beliefs, and inclinations toward integration should be highlighted. Technology integration should be viewed as a cultural transformation rather than a mechanical process. Kurt Seemann (2003), "Holistic Technology Education," argues that technology educators should be holistic in their grasp of technology as well as in their curriculum, assessment system, and means of delivery. In NSW, two good examples are the transition from Engineering Science to Engineering Studies, where social/ethical and environmental concerns must be learned, and the new and coming 2003 Design and Technology 7–10 syllabus, which describes "holistic solutions." This work promotes historical and theoretical research and articulates classroom practice adjustments for holistic technology education, with a focus on providing a grounded frame of reference to facilitate student learning and understanding of any technological activity and decision event. As a result, a First Principles framework for structuring learning for holistic comprehension of design technology and processes is offered.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the concept related to holistic education and technology.
- 2) To know about the latest trends in digital transformation and educational technology.
- 3) To study the India initiatives for education sector.
- 4) To know the technology in education application model in India.

Holistic Education

Holistic education is supported for all learners, yet this situation has shown resistance to change over time due to power dynamics. Technology can help by raising awareness and sharing the truth. In holistic education, the teacher seeks to work with the whole student, including physical, emotional, intellectual, aesthetic, moral, and spiritual elements. The teacher, in particular, tries to blend analytic and intuitive thinking, or the right and left sides of the brain. A holistic approach to education is concerned with the intellectual, emotional, social, physical, artistic, creative, and spiritual potentials of each individual. It aims to involve students in the teaching and learning process and to instill personal and collective responsibility in them.

Benefits of Holistic Education

Holistic education is based on a learning paradigm that benefits students, teachers, schools, and communities. Students are given the tools they need to better their educational performance and develop the life skills required for a successful professional career.

- 1) **Improved Academic Achievement:** By adapting to individual learning styles and providing a supportive learning environment, holistic education can improve the academic results of all children, regardless of background or circumstances. When students feel physically and emotionally protected and connected to others, their brain powers rise.
- 2) **Enhanced Mental and Emotional Well-Being:** Students have a better chance of emerging with self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of social duty in a supportive setting where social and emotional development is stressed alongside academics.
- 3) **Increased Problem-Solving Ability:** Students who are challenged to solve real-world problems in their communities develop strong critical-thinking abilities. These hands-on projects teach students skills that will be useful in their adult jobs, such as data collection, analysis, and reporting, as well as collaboration with others.
- 4) **Reduced Impact of Inequities:** The whole-child approach to education has been found to lessen the psychological impact of issues such as violence, abuse, or poverty on academic achievement by emphasizing integrated learning principles.

The Importance of Holistic Approaches

Many students fail to understand educational curriculum information, and conventional treatment only provides partial relief for many human diseases and illnesses. In a world of pandemics, understanding how our moods, emotions, personalities, and relationships affect health and education is becoming increasingly important. The placebo response, which occurs when an inert medicine, therapy, or management has a positive effect, is at the heart of research and provides evidence of the power of mind over body. Belief and faith are seen as the driving forces at work here.

Digital Transformation and EdTech

Over 47% of learning management products will be AI-enhanced within the next three years, according to the eLearning Industry. Though AI has been present in the EdTech industry for some time in the form of adaptive learning, interactive games for early childhood education, learning management systems, student metrics analysis, and other applications, schools and educational institutions were slow to adopt these technologies prior to the pandemic. With fast digitalization on the rise, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to promote tech-enabled and enhanced learning environments for students is predicted to gain popularity in the near future. Another developing trend that will have a considerable impact on the Ed-Tech industry's transition is school automation. As more educational institutes and platforms seek to transition to a completely digital environment, software developers will seek to provide comprehensive ecosystems that integrate all operational and non-operational components of a school's operation on a single platform or application. This is beneficial not just to the institutions but also to the students, teachers, and parents, who will benefit from real-time information, improved teaching tools, and superior learning experiences. Education for all is a global incentive for the Ed-Tech business, ensuring ease of access to every student worldwide. The epidemic paved the way for the Ed Tech industry's rapid growth while demonstrating its potential to secure education for everyone. The global EdTech market was assessed at \$254.80 billion in 2021, according to a report by Research and Markets. It is estimated to reach \$605.40 billion by 2027, growing at a CAGR of 15.52%. The key themes influencing the transformation of EdTech organisations will be technical advancements, industrial skill requirements, and the demand for the supply

of a richer curriculum for learners.

India's Initiatives for Education

Education is a fundamental right that is required to promote sustainable development. The importance of ICT in classroom learning has been improved and augmented, and it is a crucial instrument in providing quality education for all. A decent education throughout the lifecycle, from early childhood to adulthood, may be a liberating process for individuals and a leveller and equaliser within society. India has also made significant progress toward the aim of "Education for All" in recent years. From the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan through the Right to Education Bill, the emphasis has been on ensuring children's equal access to quality education. ICT has played a crucial role in facilitating this shift. The New Education Policy 2020 (NEP) acknowledges the value of technology in assisting teachers, crossing the language barrier between teachers and students, producing digital libraries, popularising language learning, and ensuring broader access to education.

The EdTech trend is growing globally and in India

According to an IEBF research, the Indian EdTech business was valued at US\$ 750 million in 2020 and is predicted to grow to US\$ 4 billion by 2025 at a CAGR of 39.77%. The growth of the EdTech industry in India is fueled by a variety of factors, one of which is the increased demand for tech-based courses. Students in grades K–12, professionals looking to upskill through non-academic courses, students pursuing higher education, and students preparing for competitive tests are the primary contributors to EdTech demand. On a worldwide scale, the same increasing trend is evident, with identical variables driving the need for tech-supported learning. A crucial component is a shift in the way education is approached. Rather than using chalk and discussion, educators prefer to use digital tools to complement the curriculum and create an engaging environment for students. Technology advancements and the advent of concepts such as transmedia education, gamification, and digitization are both responsible for fueling the EdTech business.

Technology in Education: NDEAR

NDEAR stands for National Digital Education Architecture, with a mission to develop a "single national digital infrastructure to energise and catalyse the education ecosystem." Essentially, this is a technology framework that tries to enable existing systems to be upgraded and compatible while also making common building blocks and services available for the development of new tools and solutions. NDEAR's goal is to stimulate and catalyse the digital education ecosystem through these common buildings and services. It is a distributed, adaptive, and open socio-technical system with self-organization, scalability, and sustainability qualities.

(Source: secondary data)

Holistic Technology Application Model

Holistic technology is a method of managing information technology that focuses on understanding and treating a complex computer system as a single unit.

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(Sources: secondary data; positive climate; teacher learning community)

A Model of Holistic Education

As experiential learning augments opportunities for students to connect with stakeholders of diverse organisations as part of their course curriculum, the holistic education model has the strength to empower students to build multi-stakeholder sensitivity. A holistic education model seeks to imbibe the highest standard of multi-disciplinary teaching and research established by ancient Indian universities such as Takshashila, Nalanda, and Vikramshila, which allows students to have multiple options for courses of study as well as instil a variety of skills in them to become well-versed in multiple careers.

(Source: Rajita Kulkarni)

The NEP-2020 holistic education model strives to merge the borders of many educational fields. The process of reengineering the education system, from understanding the purpose of education to achieving the desired outcomes of education, must be flexible enough to allow for the breaking down of current silos. It advocates for regulatory body autonomy and decentralisation in order to strengthen HEIs.

Conclusion

To be on the bleeding edge of educational innovation, a combination of design thinking, lean thinking, and agile thinking will be required, ultimately optimising student accomplishment and progress. Blended learning, which makes use of a variety of technological devices, can bring a broader, more flexible approach to all topical learning, supporting deeper, more tolerant thinkers. Academics are increasingly being fired for their opinions if they disagree with senior management, and this behaviour is harmful to a constructive, progressive society. To bring to light a crucial aspect of hybrid learning and its efficacy in 21st century education. To get more holistic results, both students and teachers must utilise digital solutions. With Blackboard Learn by Anthology, educators can be confident that they have laid the groundwork for an EdTech ecosystem that allows all students and teachers to create more personalised learning experiences that support student success while improving efficiency and preparing their institution for the future of higher education. The rapid advancement of technology, which is now integrated into almost every facet of life, has intensified throughout the epidemic, resulting in polarised perspectives and human conflicts. The holistic application of technology for educational innovation Using new technology holistically could speed up personalised and individualised learning in the twenty-first century. It must be sensitive to their students' qualities and actively respond to the needs of the future. As a result, students should be able to access and manage a variety of opportunities to select and implement the appropriate level of educational programmes, including technology-enabled learning.

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References

- [1] Abbitt, J. T. (2011). An investigation of the relationship between self-efficacy beliefs about technology integration and technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) among preservice teachers. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 27(4), 134-143.
- [2] June Lee, Yong-Lyun Kim, Eun Young Jang (2020), "Becoming a Smart School: A Holistic View of Technology Integration", *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*. 14(5), www.ijicc.net
- [3] Kaladevi, P. S. (2020), "Holistic Development of Education", *International Journal of Advanced Research and Emerging Trends (JARET)*, 1(3), 1-5
- [4] Kurt Seemann (2003), "Basic Principles in Holistic Technology Education", *Journal of Technology Education*, 14(2), 26-39.
- [5] Rajita Kulkarni (2021), "Holistic Learning in Higher Education Institutions in India-A Sustainable Approach", *National Education Policy - 2020: Transforming Higher Education in India*, Essay No. 24, pp. 1-18 ISBN No. 81-7520-162-2.
- [6] Şule Betül Tosuntaş, Zühal Çubukçu, Tuğba İnci (2019), "A Holistic View to Barriers to Technology Integration in Education", *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*, 10(4), 439-461, DOI: 10.17569/tojqi.613969
- [7] <https://www.cxotoday.com/interviews/innovative-tech-and-holistic-learning-is-the-new-era/>
- [8] [8.https://elearningindustry.com/human-nature-influenced-by-technology-part-2-holistic-approach-education](https://elearningindustry.com/human-nature-influenced-by-technology-part-2-holistic-approach-education)

PREDICTION OF HANDBALLPLAYING ABILITY FROM SELECTED PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG COLLEGE LEVELMENHAND PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to predict Handball playing ability from selected Psychological variables among college level Handball players. To achieve the purpose of the study, the investigator selected 100 colleges Handball players from different colleges. In this study the Handball playing ability was predicted from 100 College Handball Players with the help of selected Predictor variables Namely Psychological variables such as Anxiety, Aggression, Achievement motivation and Self Confidence. The Handball playing ability was determined by subjective rating by 3 experts and was as the Criterion variables . The Backward multiple regression method was used to determine the prediction equation (Thomas and Nelson 1990). Based on the limitation and delimitation of the present Research study, it was concluded that I. the handball playing ability could be bet predicted from psychological variables namely Anxiety. Aggression, Achievement and Self Confidence.

Introduction

Handball

Handball is played by two teams composed of six players and a goal keeper each, who try and throw the ball into their opponents' gal Since the basis of the game is catching, throwing, jumping and shooting at goal. Handball is sport that develops the bodies of young players as well as keeping older players fit.

Psychological variables

The world psychology derived from the Greek 'psycho' means mind or soul 'logy' means science. So the world psychology is the science of mind and soul. Psychology studies human nature science of the mind and soul. Psychology plays the major role in sports and closely associated with psychological components.

Anxiety

Anxiety is complex emotional state characterized by a general fear of fore bonding usually accompanied by tension. It often as to do with inter personal relation. Social situation and feeling of rejection and insecurity and usually a part of anxiety.

Aggression

Accidental harm is not aggression, but acts that are intended to injure others for aggression, whether or not they are successful.

Achievement motivation

Achievement motivation refers to the tendency to strive to achieve and to excel in whatever challenge that is presented in a particular game or sport.

Self confidence

Self Confidence is the belief that one can successfully perform a desired behavior. The desired behavior might be kicking a soccer gal, staying in an exercise regime, recovering from a knee injury, service an ace. But the common factor is that one believes that he will get the job done.

Methodology

The purpose of study was to predict playing ability in handball from selected psychological variables among college level handball players. To achieve the purpose of the study, the investigator selected hundred college handball players different colleges.

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Results and Discussions

In this study the handball playing ability was predicted from hundred college handball players with help of selected predictor variables such as anxiety, aggression, self confidence and achievement motivation. The handball playing ability was determined by subjective rating by three experts and was used as the criterion variables.

Table I The variable selected for prediction with BETA and 't' values for model 12 for handball playing ability

	Variable	Beta in	T	Sig	Partial Correlation	Co linearity statistics
12						Tolerance
	Anxiety	-0.259	-4.184	0.000	-0.405	0.511
	Aggression	-0.144	-2.973	0.004	-0.301	0.830
	Achievement motivation	0.124	1.971	0.052	0.204	0.490
	Self Confidence	-0.118	-2.470	0.015	-0.253	0.854

Table -I shows the partial correlation between handball playing ability and selected predictor variables Anxiety, Aggression Self Confidence and Achievement motivation were -0.405, -0.301, -0.253, 0.204 respectively which are significant at 0.01 level.

Table II multiple correlation, R square, R square change and significance of the selected predictor variables by backward selectors.

S.No	Variable Predicted	R	R Square	F Change	ANOVA 'F'	Significance of F change
1	Left wing shot					
2	Anxiety					
3	Aggression	0.909	0.826	1.907	42.358	0.171
4	Achievement Motivation					
5	Self Confidence					
6	Right wing shot					

Table -II shows the selected predictor variable by backward regression method i.e Model 12 from Table -II are presented namely Anxiety, Aggression, Achievement Motivation and Self Confidence. The multiple correlation are 0.909 with R square value of 0.826 F change 1.907 ANOVA 'F' 42.358 with the significant 'F' change 0.171 are presented in the above table. The significant 'F' change of 0.171 with the set significance level of 0.10 where all the other variable were removed from the equation.

Conclusion

Based on the limitation and delimitation of the present research study, it was concluded that the Handball playing ability could be Best predicted from Psychological variables such as Anxiety, Aggression, Achievement Motivation and Self Confidence.

TECHNOLOGY IN HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

Technologies have been deeply influencing the lifestyle of the people in the modern world. They, on the one hand, allure people to get involved with all the new gadgets, yet, on the otherhand, force them to focus on what is important and appropriate for their lives. In this sense, technology is a power full tools, for it offers humans great possibilities and at the same time, it confines them in what they do and how they do it. For instance, new technologies in the form of websites and online channels enable people to access enormous loads of information. However, due to the lack of constraints on what sort of information and content is made available online, people constantly need to rely on their judgment to select what's relevant. This selection requires a certain degree of media literacy and self-discipline. Thus, given the reality of the paradox of technology, the liberal course in holistic life education gains an added significance. Holistic education is said to encompass a wide range of philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices, with a special emphasis on wholeness and integration. Therefore, this paper tried to elucidate the continued importance of holistic life education in technology.

Keywords: *Technology Paradox, Holistic Education, Philosophy of Life*

Introduction

It is an undeniable fact that modern lifestyle, economy, educational system, social interactions, and personal development have changed dramatically with ever-advancing, more ingenious, and easily accessible technologies. Such technological progress allures people to get involved with all the new gadgets, yet forces them to be selective and to focus on what is important and appropriate for their lives. If people are not able to filter the use of technologies, they get distracted, confused, and eventually lead a life that is less efficient and less meaningful. In this sense, technology is a paradox, for it offers humans great possibilities and at the same time, it confines them in what they do and how they do it. For instance, new technologies in the form of websites and online channels enable us to access enormous loads of information. However, due to a lack of constraints on what sort of information and content is made available online, people constantly need to rely on their judgment to select what's relevant. This selection requires a certain degree of media literacy and self-discipline. People also get lazy and live sedentary lives by using various gadgets, which in turn curtails the potential use of their brains. There is also a danger of becoming dependent on and even getting addicted to gadgets. In other words, with the use of boundless and easy communication through social media, people tend to forget how great and valuable are interpersonal relations. Besides, when communication is processed through different mediated channels, the messages will never be as rich and clear as those that occur in face to face interactions, which further lead to misunderstandings and interpersonal conflicts. Besides, being connected online with everyone, in any place and at any time makes it difficult to live in the here and now, and leads to losing contact with oneself and the people we care about. When people spend so much time in virtual worlds, they may lose touch with the real world.

Thus, given the reality of the paradox of technology, the liberal course in holistic life education gains an added significance. Holistic education, which began as a movement in response to the dominant "mechanistic" worldview of mainstream education, is said to encompass a wide range of philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices, with a special emphasis on wholeness and integration. As an eclectic and inclusive movement, it attempts to avoid excluding any significant aspects of the human experience and foster more dynamic and holistic views of reality. Holistic education also proposes that educational experiences promote a more balanced development of the intellectual, physical, religious, and spiritual, affective and emotional, relational and social, and aesthetic and ecological aspects of an individual. The holistic education concept of the philosophy in educating the whole person, beyond core academics is gaining steam in learning circles as schools struggle to improve student outcomes. Many organizations are realizing that students need more than just a strong foundation in a core curriculum, they also need to be supported by a community and to develop a compassionate understanding of the world around them. State governments and school district officials set the tone for whether learning environments will focus on academic-centric or holistic learning concepts. However, teachers play the central role in enacting learning policies, and they have the greatest opportunity to help students discover their

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identities and find meaning in community and world connections through holistic teaching methods. By pursuing a Master of Education in Education Policy and Leadership or a Master of Arts in Teaching, educators can learn how holistic learning and other teaching strategies can shape students' futures.

What is Holistic Education?

Holistic education is a comprehensive approach to teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. Emphasis is placed on positive school environments and providing whole-child supports (services that support academic and nonacademic needs, also known as wraparound supports) to students. Students are taught to reflect on their actions and how they impact the global and local community, as well as how to learn from the community around them. Teachers often engage students in projects that apply critical-thinking skills toward solving real-world problems.

History of Holistic Education, Methods and Educational Model

Holistic education is a relatively new movement developed in the 1980s to counteract the existing US learning structure that was perceived as mechanistic, according to Education Corner. However, the theory of educating based on a person's entire experience has roots in ancient concepts of instruction, including those of Greek and native indigenous cultures, and has increased in prevalence over the past century. Several different approaches based on whole-person education gained steam in the 20th century, including Maria Montessori's self-motivated growth philosophy and Rudolf Steiner and Emil Molt's Waldorf experiential learning technique. Many states are now incorporating holistic goals into their educational system improvement plans. This trend is encouraged by the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA), which provides federal funding to foster state efforts. School systems are increasingly accepting the theory that learning conditions, whole-child services, and social and emotional development are measurable variables of education and can improve equity and outcomes, according to Education Counsel.

Holistic Education Methods

The goal of holistic education is to cultivate a developing child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual attributes. Serving the whole child means providing opportunities that are personalized to a child's skills and feelings. Lessons are conducted in a safe, supportive environment that allows students to utilize their individual strengths. Teachers must be prepared to nurture students with varying educational levels and learning capabilities. While holistic education is guided by one overarching philosophy, teachers may employ a number of methods and strategies to create a holistic learning culture.

Educational Models of Holistic Education

Experiential Learning: Schools focused on experiential learning provide hands-on educational experiences. For instance, students might work in groups exploring different learning styles to determine which styles are most effective for them. Holistic, experiential techniques often include problem-solving exercises to address community problems or create innovative products.

(i) **Self-Guided Learning:** In self-guided educational environments, teachers allow students to learn at their own pace in the style that best suits them. The self-guided culture allows for personalization to mitigate the inadequacies of one-size-fits-all learning models. Low-stakes assessments are used to adjust the curriculum's content and pace. Classrooms may be smaller and contain students of different ages and ability levels.

(ii) **Community Schools:** Community schools are based on the idea that people find meaning through connections with their community. Teachers partner with community members, including families, residents, organizations, and officials, to provide integrated support and expanded learning opportunities, including after-school and summer programs. Schools are a hub of the community bringing together academic, social, development, and engagement activities.

(iii) **Interdisciplinary Coursework:** Part of what makes up holistic education is the idea that students' cognitive growth is improved when multiple subjects are addressed together. Some schools are creating integrated programs where teachers from different disciplines come together to teach thematic courses that address issues from multiple perspectives. Coursework might also include independent research, travel, fieldwork, and internships.

Teacher Strategies of Holistic Education

Strong Student-Teacher Relationships: When teachers are able to form strong bonds with students,

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performance and engagement is positively impacted. At-risk students have a higher chance of success when they feel safe and nurtured. Teachers can foster strong relationships by responding to students' strengths and needs and by acting in a culturally sensitive manner. Allowing students to help develop classroom rules and take on leadership roles helps encourage trust and communication among students and enhances their motivation to succeed. Encouraging Self-Confidence: Students need to believe that they belong at school and have the ability to succeed. Teachers can help build self-confidence by providing multiple opportunities for students to digest structured information and communicate their understanding in a variety of ways. Teachers must recognize students' unique strengths and treat all students equally. Student motivation can be enhanced by making sure that lessons are relevant to students' lives and focus on realistic issues. Incorporating Emotional Reflection: As a teacher, it's not always easy to look beyond academic performance to nurture the mental and emotional well-being of a child. To encourage emotional reflection in daily routines, teachers might provide moments for students to reflect, contemplate, or meditate. Lessons to teach empathy could focus on effective listening and observation techniques or literature that presents varying perspectives on social issues.

Benefits of Holistic Education

Holistic education is based on a learning philosophy that brings a number of benefits to students, teachers, schools, and communities. Students are empowered to improve their educational outcomes and gain the life skills necessary to take on a successful professional career. Improved Academic Achievement: Holistic education can improve the academic achievements of all children, regardless of background and circumstances, by catering to individual learning styles and providing a supportive learning environment. Children's brain capacities are increased when they feel physically and emotionally safe and connected to others, according to the Learning Policy Institute. Enhanced Mental and Emotional Well-Being: In a supportive environment, where social and emotional learning is emphasized along with academics, students have a better chance of emerging with self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of social responsibility. Increased Problem-Solving Ability: Students who are tasked with solving real-world problems that exist in their communities emerge with strong critical-thinking skills. These hands-on projects give students skills that will apply to their adult careers, such as how to gather, analyze, and report data and how to collaborate with others. Reduced Impact of Inequities: By emphasizing integrated learning concepts, the whole-child approach to education has been shown to reduce the psychological impact of issues such as violence, abuse, or poverty on academic achievement, according to the Learning Policy Institute.

Holistic Education vs Traditional Education

The different between the Holistic education claims that:

- 1) It focuses on the physical, emotional, intellectual, spiritual and social development of the student.
- 2) The teacher plays the role of a facilitator to induce development in students
- 3) It enhances and develops the cognitive and creative sides of its students and helps students discover an identity, purpose and meaning in connection to the community.
- 4) It is an integrated education system that is transformative in nature and the entire system is skill and knowledge oriented.
- 5) There is a strong collaborative relationship among students, parents and teachers.
- 6) It tries to cultivate a constructive approach, Gandhi's Basic Education, Value Education and Peace Education.
- 7) It is more relevant to the life of the student as a whole and makes use of classrooms that promote active learning.
- 8) It provides a great level of freedom of the mind and heart while focusing on the artistic, academic and practical aspects of learning.
- 9) It also helps in developing inspiration, imagination and intuition in its students while focusing on a curriculum that values the interests, needs and ability of its students.

On the other Hand, Traditional Education According to Critics

- 1) Focuses primarily on intellectual development while giving the teacher autocratic power.
- 2) Favours memorization and is an exam-oriented system.
- 3) Has a system that places a number of restrictions on students and is a dominating system that rewards only those that conform to the rules.
- 4) Is highly programmed and mechanized and can include learning that has no practical

- applications in one's life.
- 5) Is a system that has no child-based curriculum and makes way for fewer classroom interactions when compared to the holistic education system.
 - 6) The system is designed to meet modern industrial requirements that promote passive learning.
 - 7) Is highly teacher-centred and is a final evaluation based system.

Technology and Education

The advancement of technology seems to have an impact on all aspects of people's lives. But, has technology impacted education? Has technology changed how the educators instruct and how the pupils learn? A look at the 14th century depiction by Laurentus de Volition (Wikimedia, 2020) of a university lecturer in medieval Italy may seem to depict that modern education remains much the same as it has been for many centuries.

Once upon a time lecturer is instructing from a podium at the front of the classroom while the students sit in rows. Some of the students appear to be following the lecture with open books in front of them, whereas a few are looking bored, some others are chatting with their neighbors, and one even appears to be sleeping. Modern-day classrooms do not look much different, except that the students look at their gadgets instead of books, eat, chat, and even sleep comfortably. Hence, a cynic would say that all the advances in technology have done practically nothing to impact education (Purdue, 2020). However, on the other hand, as the observations and practicalities of the modern-day classrooms indicate, technology has impacted and continues to impact the understanding of education, and the imparting and acquisition of knowledge.

Pre-Independence Period (1813-1947): India under the British Rule-The interplay of imperial and domestic education in the country had mostly led to disengagement during the British period. Tracing back the use of educational technology during the colonial era, it was not before 1930s, when British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) aired cultural and educational programs in the country through broadcast radio. In 1937, All India Radio (AIR) broadcasted educational programs for school children (Bharati, 2014, Agarwal, 2005). This period gave birth to educational radio in India. **1947-1970s: Placing Educational Technology Post-Independence-** Several government educational initiatives have been launched since the independence of the country in 1947. The Educational potentials and limitations of Radio and Television were explored. Emphasis was also laid on reviewing audio instructional methods of teaching in classrooms from the underlying psychological perspectives (Reddy, 1975).

1980s-2000: Gaining momentum - This period witnessed the beginning of indigenous materials and methods. Instructional media packages for teaching and learning were introduced in the Indian schools. Technology teacher training got impetus and educational technology at schools was linked with urban and rural development initiatives. **2000s-Present: The new Millennium March-** Educational research looked into the scope and limitation of information technology. Right to Education got implemented in 2010 with an aim of universalization of primary education in the country. Laptops and tablets along with whiteboards and smart boards were introduced in the private and public schools of India. Contrary to classroom technology integration, this era also saw development like 'Hole in the Wall' experiments and One Laptop per Child initiatives which received worldwide attention. Trends were also seen towards para-teachers reaching out to children in the several slum communities of the country where schools were absent or dysfunctional. Foundations and educational non-profit organizations grew immensely. This millennium is also witnessing strong educational technology focused corporate-academic partnership. Huge emphasis is being laid on quality education. M-Learning is increasingly being explored in classrooms and stress is on technological pedagogical integration in teaching and learning.

Impact of Modern Technology on Education

Technology has changed the way we live our lives by deeply impacting different facets of life. Several complex and critical processes are being carried out with ease and greater efficiency with the help of modern technology (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). Technology continues to introduce profound changes in the everyday life of people. There is a rush to embrace every new gadget as soon as it comes into the market. Both individuals and institutions are being encouraged to advance the development of technology, consume them, and learn to fit into the thought processes and behavioral patterns dictated by the interlocking systems of technology (Bowers, 1998), thus making them either just believe or truly become competent in using many technologies (Feenberg, 2010). Technology has also revolutionized the field of education.

In other words, the trend in technological advancement and its widespread consumerism seems to turn skills, relationships, and knowledge into commodities. Further, the use of technology appears to commodify even

more aspects of individual and community life. All technologies amplify certain aspects of individual experience and cultural values while reducing some other aspects and even losing them entirely from awareness. For example, computers tend to amplify forms of context-free knowledge but overlook contextualized experiences. Technologies tend to amplify a conduit view of language but fail to recognize the metaphorical nature of language. Gadgets tend to amplify the view that individuals are autonomous decision-makers while obfuscating the importance of relationships in creating shared knowledge. The people tend to see technologies as almost natural to living, but they are determined by the meanings people give them. The further, educational institutions are indoctrinating the students into believing that technology-mediated learning and communication represent a superior and empowered form of education. Educational institutions also fail to help their students recognize that objective data of information represent another person's specific way of knowing and interpreting (Bowers, 1998). Thus, given both the advantages and disadvantages of the role of technology in education, it is not a surprise to say that technology, particularly in the field of education, is paradox.

Conclusion

Ongoing technological progress continues to allure every segment of the modern world that people from all spheres get engaged with various types of gadgets, both enhancing and disturbing their lives. For instance, new technologies provide us with easy access to loads of useful information, yet constrain us from developing analytical and reflective skills, thus requiring the users of technology to develop a certain degree of technology literacy. Or, people use technology to communicate, but when misused, the messages lead to misunderstandings and interpersonal conflicts, thus requiring the users to have some sort of self-discipline. Further, when people spend so much time in the virtual world, there is a danger to lose touch with reality. This is the paradox of technology, which consists of at the same time dealing with the whole and the parts, complexity and simplicity, diversity and unity, good and evil, control and freedom, needs and wants, connection and isolation, means and ends, so on. Thus, given this reality of the paradoxes of technology, the liberal course in holistic life education becomes paramount in training and guiding people to avoid excluding any significant aspects of the human experience and foster a more dynamic and holistic view of life. This study holds significance not just as providing background information about the development and integration of technology in Indian schools but also lays down the foundation for present and future initiatives and research. The study is a contribution towards looking over the decades to add to the limited school educational technology research available and provide a compilation document to tactfully carve the roadmap towards positive integration of technology in Indian classrooms.

References

- [1] Agrawal, B. C. (2005). Educational media in India. In U. V. Reddi & S. Mishra (Eds.), *Perspectives on distance education: educational media in Asia*. Vancouver, B.C.: Commonwealth of Learning.
- [2] Bharati, G (2014). Development and implementation of ICT aided constructivist learning approach for the professional development of pre-service teachers.
- [3] Byker, Erik Jon (2012). *The Bangalore Challenge: Case Studies of the social construction of technology in elementary schools*.
- [4] Devi, S, Rizwaan M. & Chander S (2012). ICT for quality of education in India. *IJPSS*. Volume 2, Issue 6.
- [5] Mahmoudi, S., Jafari, E., Nasrabadi, H. A., & Liaghatdar, M. J. (2012). Holistic education: An approach for 21st century. *International Education Studies*, 5(2), 178-186. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v5n3p178>
- [6] Mick, D. G., & Fournier, S. (1998). Paradoxes of technology: Consumer cognizance, emotions, and coping strategies. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 25, 123-143. <https://doi.org/10.1086/209531>
- [7] Miller, J. P. (Ed.) (2007). *The holistic curriculum* (2nd ed.). Toronto, ON, Canada: OISE Press.
- [8] Miller, R. (2000). Beyond reductionism: The emerging holistic paradigm in education. *The Humanistic Psychologist*, 28(1-3), 382-393. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08873267.2000.9977003>
- [9] Philosophy of Life. (2017). Holistic education center. <http://www.hec.fju.edu.tw/FJU-eng/index2.htm>

ANXIETY MANAGEMENT THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Introduction

Anxiety disorder, however are different. They can cause such distress that it interferes with a persons ability to lead a normal life. It is often accompanied by muscular tension restlessness, fatigue and problems in concentration. Anxiety disorders are partly genetic but may also be due to drugs use including alcohol and caffeine, as well as withdrawal from certain drugs. common treatment option include lifestyle changes, therapy and medication. Performance anxiety is not uncommon in sports, as to some extent fear of performance helps in achieving desired concentration. However ,the excess will lead to a rush heart beat rate. You lose concentration ,your action become disjointed and you feel paralyzed at the beginning of an important sporting event. These are symptoms o performance anxiety.

Types of Anxiety Disorder

There are several major types of anxiety disorder, each with its own characteristics. People with generalize anxiety disorder have recurring fears or worries, such as about health of fitness, and they often have persistent sense that something bad is just about to happens. Panic disorder involves sudden, intense and unprovoked feelings of terror and dread. A related disorder involves phobias, or intense fears, about certain object or situation. Specific phobias may involve things such as encountering certain animals flying in airplane. Social phobias involve fear of social settings or public places. Obsessive-compulsive disorder is characterized by persistent uncontrollable and unwanted feelings or thoughts (obsession) and routine or rituals (compulsions) which individuals engage to try to prevent or rid themselves of these thoughts. Someone who suffers severe physical or emotional trauma such as from a nature disaster or serious or crime may experience post-traumatic stress disorder.

Symptoms of Anxiety Disorder

Symptoms vary depending on the type of anxiety disorder, but general symptoms include.

- 1) Feelings of panic, fear, and uneasiness
- 2) Problems sleeping
- 3) Cold or sweaty hand or feet
- 4) Shortness of breath
- 5) Heart palpitations
- 6) An inability to be still and calm
- 7) Dry mouth
- 8) Numbness or tingling in the hands or feet
- 9) Nausea
- 10) Muscle tension
- 11) Dizziness

Although they may begin at any time, anxiety disorder often surface often surface in adolescence or early adulthood. There is some evidence that anxiety disorder run in families; genes as well as early learning experiences within families seem to make some people more like than others to experience these disorders.

Causes of Anxiety Disorder

The exact cause of anxiety disorder is unknown; bit anxiety disorders likely other forms of mental illness are not the result of personal weakness, a character flaw, or post upbringing.

Effective Treatment for Anxiety Disorder

Most cases of anxiety disorder can be treated successfully by appropriately trained mental health professionals such as licensed psychologists. Research has demonstrated that the form of psychotherapy known as “cognitive-behavioral therapy” (CBT) can be highly effective in treating anxiety disorders. Although the exact treatment approach depends on the type of disorder, one or a combination of the following therapies may be used

for most anxiety disorders:

- 1) Psychotherapy: Psychotherapy (a type of counseling) addresses the emotional response to mental illness. It is a process in which trained mental health professionals help people by talking through strategies for understanding and dealing with these disorders.
- 2) Behavioral therapy: involves using technique to reduce or stop the undesired behaviors associated with these disorders.
- 3) Cognitive therapy: patient learn to understand how their though contribute to the symptoms of anxiety disorders, and how their thoughts contribute to the symptoms of anxiety disorders, and how to change those thought patterns to reduce the likelihood of occurrence and the intensity of reaction.
- 4) Medication: Drugs used to reduce symptoms of anxiety disorder include anti-depression and anxiety-reducing drugs, In case where medications are used, the patients care may be managed collaboratively by more than one provider of treatment. It is important for patients to realize that there are side effects to any drugs, which must be monitored closely by the provider who prescribe the medication.
- 5) Dietary and lifestyle changes.
- 6) Relaxation therapy.

How Does Anxiety Affect Sports Performance?

Anxiety affects a sports players performance in physiological, cognitive and behavioral ways. If you suffer from anxiety before an important athletic competition, your sports performance will be affected. Listed below are the ways in which anxiety can affect sports performance.

- 1) Fear: When you are afraid of a certain situation, you may experience body paralysis once you find yourself present in that situation. This indicates severe anxiety.
- 2) Unable to concentrate: Pre-competitive anxiety also develops as an inability to concentrate before an
- 3) Upcoming event or competition. The root cause of the inability to concentrate is feelings of apprehension. Apprehensions cause the individual to feel that they will fail or decrease their confidence in their ability.
- 4) Sweating: The anxiety makes the athlete over conscious of his situation and the apprehensions make him feel us easy. As a result, the body may feel sudden bursts of heat and will release a lot of perspiration when the body receives signals from the brain. Excessive sweating can occur anywhere on the body but mainly on the hands and the face. The individual will begin to feel uncomfortable and this merely reinforces the anxiety they are already feeling.
- 5) Racing Heart: As a result of anxiety the heart rate of an athlete may also increase manifold. This may be due to the excessive release of adrenaline in the body. Increased heart rate are also released to panic. If the athletes becoming increasingly panicked, the heart rate will also increase.
- 6) Shortness of Breath: Breathing very fast or panting is another symptom of anxiety. Sometimes the athletes experience a shortness of breath and struggle to take in oxygen. It is not uncommon for athletes to hyperventilate due to sever anxiety. This in turn can deprive the brain of enough oxygen, which would lead to dizziness and/or fainting.
- 7) Dizziness: When an athlete is suffering from severe anxiety and is panicking, the brain may not receive as much blood and oxygen as it normally does. This results in dizziness.
- 8) Shaking: Before a competition or important event, an athlete may experience sever shaking of the hands or knees. This is due to an increased spike of adrenaline in the body which is brought on by severe anxiety. If the anxiety persists, the body may collapse.

How to Prevent Performance Anxiety in Sports Performance?

- 1) Diaphragmatic Breathing: The diaphragm is a muscle between the chest and the stomach cavity. The breathing done by contracting this muscle is known as diaphragmatic breathing.
- 2) Relaxation Technique: When the athlete feels the symptoms of anxiety such as increased heart rate, increased blood pressure or difficult breathing, a relaxation technique can help in controlling the anxiety.
- 3) Visualization: Visualization is a technique, used by the athletes to control their anxiety. In this

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technique one visualizes himself in a situation similar to the actual event. The athlete visualizes himself winning in front of the entire crowd where the event is to take place.

- 4) Muscle Relaxation: Anxiety results in stiffness of the muscles. Muscle relaxing practices are done to avoid this happening during the actual game.
- 5) Focusing on What Can Be Controlled: Athletes should remind themselves that they are better trained, they have developed better techniques, but should not try to control things that are not in their control such as the audience or the opponent.

Overcoming Performance Anxiety

There are also mental tricks you can play to help you perform with less anxiety. They include:

- 1) Focus on the friendliest faces in the audience.
- 2) Laugh when you can, it can help you relax.
- 3) Make yourself look good. When you look good, you feel good.

These tips should help reduce performance anxiety. But if they don't, talk to counselor or therapist trained in treating anxiety issues. You may benefit from more intensity therapy, such as cognitive behavioral therapy, to help overcome performance anxiety. The addition, medications, such as beta-blockers, a heart medicine that lowers heart rate and sometimes used by people with performance anxiety. Confronting your fears and learning ways to reduce and manage them can be empowering. Not only will it make you feel good about yourself, you may discover that you are a more confident performer, too.

Conclusion

In the end of this paper suggest that the sports person, individual and society all have to relief from anxiety and achieve excellence in their own field through physical education and sports. Physical education and sports not only as a part of programme to reduce, anxiety but also as a way to attaining other goals.

Reference

- [1] Heyward, Vivian H., (2002), Advanced Fitness Assessment and Exercise Prescription. (4ED), Champaign Illinois: Human Kinetics Publishers Inc.
- [2] Seligman, M.E.P.; Walker, E.F.; Rosenhan, D.L..Abnormal psychology (4th ed). Newyork: W.W. Norton& Company.
- [3] Spielberger, C.D.,Sydeman, S.J. (1994). State-Trait Anxiety Inventory and State-Trait Anger Expression Inventory.

INFLUENCE OF YOGA FOR GENERAL FITNESS FOR ALL

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Abstract

Yoga is a very versatile physical and mental activity in that its primary focus is on developing strength, flexibility, mental stability and calmness, as well as physical and mental balance. Designing an effective yoga workout program is largely dependent on your personal fitness goals and the specific benefits you want to achieve from yoga. The type of yoga that you practice will ultimately determine the types of benefits you will receive. For instance, there are specific types of yoga that are directed at developing core strength and stability and incorporate a light aerobic workout as well. On the other hand, there are certain types of yoga that primarily focus on creating a mind-body connection and relaxing and calming the mind.

Keywords: Yoga, General Fitness, Yoga Stages

Introduction

Yoga is an ancient Indian philosophy that dates back thousands of years. It was designed as a path to spiritual enlightenment, but in modern times, the physical aspects of Hatha yoga have found huge popularity as a gentle form of exercise and stress management. There are many different varieties of yoga, but each one essentially relies on structured poses (asanas) practiced with breath awareness. The classical techniques of yoga date back more than 5,000 years. The practice of yoga encourages effort, intelligence, accuracy, thoroughness, commitment and dedication. The word yoga means 'to join or yoke together'. It brings your body and mind together, and is built on three main elements – exercise, breathing and meditation. The exercises of yoga are designed to put pressure on the glandular systems of your body, increasing your body's efficiency and total health. Breathing techniques increase breath control to improve the health and function of body and mind. The two systems of exercise and breathing prepare the body and mind for meditation, with an approach to a quiet mind that allows silence and healing from everyday stress. When practiced regularly, yoga can become a powerful and sophisticated discipline for achieving physical, mental and emotional wellbeing.

Types of Yoga

There are many different varieties of yoga, each with a slightly different slant. The most popular are Hatha, Bikram, Iyengar and Vinyasa yoga.

Asanas or Yoga Postures

Each yoga posture, or asana, is held for a period of time and linked with breathing. Generally, a yoga session begins with gentle asanas and works up to more vigorous or challenging postures. A full yoga session should exercise every part of your body and should include pranayama (breath control practices), relaxation and meditation. The different postures or asanas include:

- 1) Lying Postures
- 2) Sitting Postures
- 3) Standing Postures
- 4) Inverted Or Upside-Down Postures.

Choosing the Yoga Style

Prior to choosing the yoga style that is best aligned with your personal fitness goals, spend some time learning about the various types of yoga and the benefits of each. The different types and styles of yoga are specifically designed to address unique physical and mental aspects of the human body and mind. While virtually all yoga poses will increase an individual's strength and flexibility, there are specific types and styles of yoga that focus more intensely on strength, balance, a cardiovascular effect and flexibility. For this reason, you will want to make sure that you take the time to learn the specific details of each of the types and styles of yoga and thereafter, choose the yoga style that best supports your personal health and fitness goals. Below are several styles of yoga as well as their unique areas of focus:

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- 1) Traditional Yoga: A union of the mind and body with a focus on improving flexibility of the joints, muscles, ligaments and tendons.
- 2) Relaxing Yoga: Almost solely devoted to achieving a relaxed, centered and balanced mind.
- 3) Fast Paced Yoga: Designed to raise the heart rate and build strength.
- 4) Flexibility Yoga: Primarily focused on increasing flexibility.
- 5) Meticulous Yoga: Can encompass virtually any pose, but its primary purpose is stress reduction.
- 6) Chanting Yoga: Solely designed to reduce stress and create a centered and balanced mind.

Putting all of the Pieces Together

When designing your program, it is important to keep in mind that yoga is intended to be a fluid art that seamlessly combines a series of poses and/or a sequence of movements to promote an overall benefit to the body, mind and mind-body connection. When you define and set up your personal yoga routine, you should focus on designing a sequence of poses in an order that allows for a smooth transition from one pose to the next. Yoga is generally intended to be practiced at least five times a week. However, if you choose a fast-paced yoga style or intend for your yoga routine to facilitate weight loss, you may want to perform your yoga session every other day. In addition, it would be beneficial to vary the actual poses performed in each yoga session so that each yoga routine focuses on exercising a specific set of muscle groups. Implementing an approach of this nature will not only keep the individual muscle groups in a state of continually developing, but will increase the rate in which results are obtained. For instance, you may perform a yoga routine on Monday that primarily focuses on upper body strength and flexibility and ends with relaxing poses to calm the mind. Wednesday's yoga workout may focus on lower body strength, balance and flexibility, and end with relaxing poses to calm the mind. Alternating yoga routines under this concept has proven to be quite effective at increasing an individual's overall health, fitness, flexibility and mental well-being, all while providing an avenue for weight loss. This will increase the diversity and variety of your yoga sessions, hence improving your workouts and facilitating greater health gains. By continually modifying your yoga routine, you will be able to evaluate the effectiveness of each yoga session, and thereafter tailor your routines to a series of poses that produces the greatest health benefits. As an individual becomes more comfortable with the various yoga poses, they begin to determine which poses are best suited to addressing their personal fitness goals. By tailoring your yoga routine to the series of poses that provides the largest health benefit, you will have put together a routine that is more effective, efficient, and targeted to your specific fitness goals.

There is Always Room for Improvement

Even professional yoga instructors find that they still have to continually work to perfect their ability to perform some of the more complicated poses. This will most likely be the case for you too, as there are several yoga poses that are extremely difficult to perform. Certain yoga poses may be deemed difficult for one of the following reasons:

- 1) Flexibility requirements
- 2) Strength requirements
- 3) Balance requirements

Because of the difficulty of many yoga poses, it will be necessary to repeatedly practice the pose while continuing to develop the requirements that are preventing you from being able to complete the pose. For example, an approach to improving your ability to perform the Camel pose is listed below:

- 1) Identify the benefits of the pose: The benefits of the Camel pose are to stretch the body, improve posture and improve strength.
- 2) Identify the problem: It feels uncomfortable. You may spend too much time bent forward. This could occur because of how you normally sit at work.
- 3) Find a solution: Try making sure that your legs are in line, and use a yoga block to make the pose more comfortable.
- 4) Find another solution: When you are in the kneeling portion, ensure that your legs are the proper distance from one another.
- 5) Find a third solution: When leaning back, use a yoga block for support and as a way to gradually work into the position.

Although the art of yoga has been practiced for thousands of years and has its roots planted in Eastern culture, its popularity has increased dramatically in the United States much more recently. The benefits of yoga, both physical and mental, have been well documented by the medical industry, and will improve the quality of life

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for virtually any individual. Because of this, we have dedicated an entire section of our website to discussions solely related to the arts of yoga and meditation. For more information related to the various types and styles of yoga, the benefits of each type and style, and sample yoga routines, please visit our [yoga](#) section.

Yoga's Impact on Your Mental Health

Most individuals already know that yoga produces some kind of a calming effect. Individually, people feel better after doing the physical exercise. Mentally, people feel calmer, sharper, maybe more content. We thought it's time to see if we could pull all together to see if there's enough evidence that the benefits individual people notice can be used to help people with mental illness.

According to their findings, yoga appears to have a positive effect on:

- 1) Mild depression
- 2) Sleep problems
- 3) Schizophrenia (among patients using medication)

Health Benefits of Yoga

The practice of yoga asanas develops strength and flexibility, while soothing your nerves and calming your mind. The asanas affect the muscles, joints and skin, and the whole body – glands, nerves, internal organs, bones, respiration and the brain. The physical building blocks of yoga are the posture and the breath.

Health benefits of yoga include:

- 1) Cardiovascular system (heart and arteries) – asanas are isometric, which means they rely on holding muscle tension for a short period of time. This improves cardiovascular fitness and circulation. Studies show that regular yoga practice may help normalise blood pressure.
- 2) Digestive system – improved blood circulation and the massaging effect of surrounding muscles speeds up a sluggish digestion.
- 3) Musculoskeletal – joints are moved through their full range of motion, which encourages mobility and eases pressure. The gentle stretching releases muscle and joint tension, and stiffness, and also increases flexibility. Maintaining many of the asanas encourages strength and endurance. Weight-bearing asana may help prevent osteoporosis, and may also help people already diagnosed with osteoporosis (if practiced with care under the supervision of a qualified yoga teacher). Long-term benefits include reduced back pain and improved posture.
- 4) Nervous system – improved blood circulation, easing of muscle tension and the act of focusing the mind on the breath all combine to soothe the nervous system. Long-term benefits include reduced stress, anxiety and fatigue, better concentration and energy levels, and increased feelings of calm and wellbeing.

Yoga for People of Different Ages

Yoga is taught in classes, catering for beginners through to advanced practitioners. It is non-competitive and suitable for anyone, regardless of your age or fitness level. Your yoga teacher should carefully guide and observe you, and modify postures when necessary. An asana should never cause pain. If it hurts, ease back on the stretch or don't do it at all. It is important to keep within your physical limits. If you are over 40, haven't exercised for a long time or have a pre-existing medical condition, you should check with your doctor before starting any regular exercise routine. Pre-exercise screening is used to identify people with medical conditions that may put them at a higher risk of experiencing a health problem during physical activity. It is a filter or 'safety net' to help decide if the potential benefits of exercise outweigh the risks for you.

References

- [1] Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine Effects of Yoga Versus Walking on Mood, Anxiety, and Brain GABA Levels: A Randomized Controlled MRS Study
- [2] Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences: Yoga Breathing, Meditation, and Longevity.
- [3] National Public Radio: The Risks and Rewards of Practicing Yoga
- [4] University of Maryland Medical Center: Yoga

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELIGION, MODERN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

People think that science and religion are intrinsically incompatible. Given that technology is a by-product of science and that science cannot advance without technology, this incompatibility is also thought to apply to the relationship between religion and technology. Since the earliest ideologies developed by human civilization, there has been a link between religion, science, and technology. Science is the methodical study of a subject that unlocks the mysteries of the cosmos. The foundation of all religions is unwavering confidence in the almighty deity who created the universe. The goal of religion is to clarify man's relationship to the highest being. It functions as a kind of link between man and God. Religion is based on faith, whereas science is based on logic and experimentation. Early proponents of science and technology had to overcome several obstacles. People who had mocked science in the past started to love it and passionately support its mission. Beyond all predictions, science and technology's rapid development altered the planet's landscape. It gave them the conveniences and luxuries that no one could have imagined. Man has conquered time, space, suffering, and his environment with the aid of science and technology. It provided convenience and comfort for the body, but it downplayed the value of moral principles and spirituality. Science is undoubtedly a mixed blessing. This paper highlights the relationship between modern science, technology and religion in a lucid manner.

Before going to discuss about the relationship between science, technology and religion, one must know what exactly they are. Science is the intellectual and practical activity encompassing the systematic study of the structure and behavior of the physical and natural world. Science is the study of how and why things happen. Modern Science and technology have changed the world in countless ways. Although technology has given many positive assets that one uses every day, it has also led the population to serious problems (For example pollution, war and nuclear weapons that can kill millions of people within no time). Science aims at understanding the behavior of natural and physical world, any supernatural or abstract reasoning is not considered to be scientific since they do not pertain to the study of practical objects. Religion is the set of beliefs concerning the cause, nature and purpose of the universe. Theologians believe in the divine power and use religion as a tool to satisfy their unanswerable questions and desire to know. Many believe that religion is the central element of life in a civilization. It is a combination of beliefs that includes an ethical framework as well as an outlook on life.

Implication of Science and Technology to man's use is as old as 2500 B.C. or much earlier when the people of Indus Valley civilization came to know first time about the fire and the wheel. Wheel is the mother of all technological innovations of today and discovery of fire is the man's first experience about energy. Since then man's curiosity and meticulous efforts have helped him for new inventions and discoveries. But science and technology got its real recognition in India during the British period and were established to meet the needs and requirements of the then Govt. During 19th century, when the whole Europe passed through a phase of Industrial revolution, the Britishers also put emphasis on development of Science and Technology in India.

Science, technology and religion have different aspects of life, having their importance and value. Religion was all important and reigned supreme in every sphere of life. But gradually its place was taken by Science & Technology. Today Science is more important than religion.

Modern Science and Modern Religion Nothing described thus far is ancient history because the legacy of religious science and technology remain with us. Today, the religious impulses underlying technological advancement take two general forms: using explicit religious doctrines, particularly Christianity, to explain why technology should be pursued and using religious imagery of transcendence and redemption removed from traditional religious doctrines but without their losing any motivating power.

An example of the first can be found in modern space exploration. The father of modern rocketry, Werner Von Braun, made use of Christian millenarianism to explain his desire to send humans into space. He wrote that the world was "turned upside down" when Jesus came to earth and that "the same thing can happen again today" by exploring space. Science did not conflict with his religion, but instead confirmed it: "In this reaching of the new millennium through faith in Jesus Christ, science can be a valuable tool rather than an impediment." The "millennium" he spoke of was the End Times.

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This religious fervor was carried along by other leaders of America's space program. Jerry Klumas, once a veteran systems engineer at NASA, wrote that explicit Christianity was normal at the Johnson space center and that the increase in knowledge brought by the space program was a fulfillment of the aforementioned prophecy in Daniel.

All the first American astronauts were devout Protestants. It was common for them to engage in religious rituals or reveries when in space, and they generally reported that the experience of space flight reaffirmed their religious faith. The first manned mission to the moon broadcast back reading from Genesis. Even before astronauts stepped out onto the moon, Edwin Aldrin took communion in the capsule — this was the first liquid and first food eaten on the moon. He later recalled that he viewed the earth from a "physically transcendent" perspective and hoped that space exploration would cause people to be "awakened once again to the mythic dimensions of man."

Technology and Religion

In other sections, we examined at the question of whether or not science and technology really were incompatible with religion as is so commonly thought. It seems that they can be very compatible at times, and furthermore that the pursuit of technological advancement has often been a direct result of religion and religious aspirations.

But what should concern secularists and nonbelievers more is the fact that those religious aspirations are not always obviously religious in nature — and if they aren't so obviously religious in the traditional sense, one might not recognize a growing religious impulse within themselves. Sometimes, the desire for or promotion of technological progress has stemmed from the fundamental religious impulse to transcend humanity. While the traditional religious stories and mythology (such as explicit Christian references to Eden) may have since fallen away, the impulse remains fundamentally religious, even when this is no longer recognizable to those actively engaged in it.

For all the other-worldly goals of transcendence, however, very worldly powers have benefitted. Benedictine monks were among the first to use technology as a spiritual tool, but eventually, their status depended upon their loyalty to kings and popes — and so labor stopped being a form of prayer and became a means for wealth and taxes. Francis Bacon dreamed of technological redemption, but achieved the enrichment of the royal court and always placed the leadership of a new Eden in the hands of an aristocratic and scientific elite.

The pattern continues today: the developers of nuclear weapons, space exploration and artificial intelligence may be propelled by religious desires, but they are sustained by military financing and the results of their labors are more powerful governments, a more pernicious status quo, and a more preeminent elite of technocrats.

Technology as Religion

Technology causes problems; there is no disputing this fact, despite all our attempts to use technology to solve our problems. People keep wondering why new technologies have not solved our problems and met our needs; perhaps now, we can suggest one possible and partial answer: they were never meant to.

For many, the development of new technologies has been about transcending mortal and material concerns completely. When an ideology, a religion, or a technology is pursued the purpose of escaping the human condition where problems and disappointments are a fact of life, then it shouldn't be at all surprising when those human problems are not really solved, when human needs are not entirely met, and when new problems are produced.

This is itself a fundamental problem with religion and why technology can be a menace — especially when pursued religious reasons. For all the problems which we create for ourselves, only we will be able to solve them — and technology will be one of our principle means. What is required is not so much a change of means by abandoning technology, but a change in ideology by abandoning the misguided desire for transcending the human condition and taking flight from the world.

There are basic differences between the outlook of science, technology and religion. The outlook of science is rational. Science believes

There are basic differences between the outlook of science, technology and religion. The outlook of science is rational. Science believes in experiments and observations. It teaches its followers that nothing is to be believed until it has been proved to be true through experiment. Religion on the other hand, is a matter of faith. It teaches its followers to believe and have faith in the teachings of religious teachers.

Science and technology are the systematic knowledge of a substance which opens the secrets of the universe and aims at the victory over the forces of nature. Religion originates with unshaking faith in the supreme,

being the maker of this universe. Religion aims at elaborating man's relation with God. It is a kind of chain which unites man with God and is a way which leads a man to Salvation. Science and technology are based on reason and experiments while religion is based on faith and surrender of the self. In many ways, religion, science and technology react upon each other as their aims and objects are totally different from each other.

The story of the conflict between religion, science and technology is painful and long. The champions of science of the early stage had to face many difficulties. Galileo had to suffer hard at the hands of his countrymen for his new idea about heavenly bodies. Copernicus, who falsified the theory of rotation of the sun round the earth, had to undergo sufferings. In the 19th century, Darwin with his theory of evolution created a great excitement among the religious men. But ultimately truth came out victorious, science and technology established their position by and by. Those persons who, at the early stage, made fun of science and technology began to admire it and advocated its cause sincerely. Western civilization actively accepted the changes in science and technology, because it was a change for the better. Technology finds a way out of a less appreciated place and it is human nature to take the opportunity to better situation. Travelling becomes much more time saving by car than horse. One can save weeks of time it takes to sail a boat across the Atlantic by using aeroplanes. One no longer has to wait a week to receive news or mail. The internet has allowed the world to be interconnected at all times. It is now a globalised nation that can share information, pictures and even transfer money overseas in seconds.

The quick development of science and technology changed the face of the earth beyond expectations. It bestowed upon mankind those comforts and luxuries which nobody could even thought of. With the help of science and technology man conquered time and distance, ailments and sufferings and he became the master of his surroundings. By and by, man began to feel that he was the creator of his own destiny and faith in God was in his folly. People lost faith in heaven or hell, God or the Supreme Being. One can feel that there can be hardly any compromise between science, technology and religion. The discoveries of science and technology are the erosion in the domain of faith. As a result science, technology and religion have been in the opposite camps since the Victorian age. Science and technology deals with the material world, religion is concerned with a divine order that one imagines. Science and technology believe in things that can be proved, religion deals with spiritual ideas that can not be proved. Science and technology depends on reason, religion on intuition and inner conviction or faith. The scientists work in the laboratory of the material world, the religious teachers probe into the chamber of the inward mind. The goal of science and technology is achievement but the religion is realization. The truth of science and technology can be proved to all the so called truths of religion have to be taken on trust. So, the two worlds seem to be opposite to each other.

Indeed science and technology are the mixed blessing, as technology is a product of science and science cannot proceed without technology. However they give bodily comfort and convenience but undermined the importance of moral values and spirituality. Man became greedy, selfish and money minded. It deprived man of generosity, fellow feeling and co- operation. The gulf between the poor and the rich became wider than it was before. Now people have began to realize the evil effects of science and technology and have felt the need of religion in human life. The religion may be destroyed by science and technology but there is one religion which science and technology can never destroy. That is the Universal religion which is based on eternal virtues like goodness, truth and generosity. Outwardly religion and science are the two opposite poles of man's consciousness. But the two do not necessarily repel each other. The meeting point is still in the minds of men.

References

- [1] Abd-El-Khalick, F. (2005). Developing deeper understandings of nature of science: The impact of philosophy of science course on pre-service science teachers' views and instructional planning. *International Journal of Science Education*, 27(1), 15-42.
- [2] Akcay, H. & Yager, R. E. (2010). The impact of Science/Technology/Society teaching approach on student learning in five domains. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 19(6), 602-611.
- [3] Brooke, J.H. (1991): *Science and Religion: Some Historical Science and Perspectives*. Cambridge University Press. Singh, Y.P (1976): *College Essays*.
- [4] Prakashan Kendra, Lucknow. Tambiah, Starley J (1990): *Magic, Science, Religion and the scope of Rationality*. Cambridge University Press.

LEARNER AUTONOMY: A POSITIVE WASH ON CLASSROOM TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Introduction

Many governments worldwide have set up committees to examine this problem and come up with some recommendations. English has come to stay in India, but its role has become one of the common medium of everyday communication. In order to make purposeful learning it's imperative to create autonomy.

Creating Autonomy

Teaching English in India is both challenging and rewarding. It is important not to forget the purpose of learning. The term 'learning' has now come to enhance the mere mastery of facts and knowledge on the part of the pupils. It has come to be acknowledged by all, that role of the teacher is to facilitate learning rather than impart mere information. The teacher should attempt to understand the difficulties of the pupil and they should be helped to self-direct their learning by creating a proper learning ambiance. There are two ways in which the teacher can improve the student's chances of successful learning. By creating a productive work atmosphere in the classroom and a good relationship with the class. Empathizing to the needs of an individual student, recognizing that every student is different with various needs and problems.

If the teacher uses English most of the time, it gives students a practice in listening and responding to spoken English. This will help them to elicit words and expressions beyond the language of the textbook. Even the texts use language that is often unnatural and artificial.

But real-life situations that occur in the classroom such as a student arriving late, someone forgetting a book etc. gives them an opportunity for real natural language to be used. The second option is, the teacher can prompt individual student to talk more about things they have done. Teacher can get students to talk and rise questions. Example: Rajath went to a party, ask him some questions about it.

Student 1: What did you eat?

Student 2: Was it a good party?

Student 3: Where there many people at the party? and so on.

In a large class it may be necessary to organize the conversation more, so that the whole class is involved. Everybody thinks of one question to ask Rajath and his party? This style of teaching helps students in Communicative English which creates an opportunity for real language practice and a learning ambiance in the class. The more important aspect of this method is to establish contact with the class and to create a comfortable learning environment for the students. If there is a formal or a casual meeting, we begin a conversation to establish a friendly atmosphere. This similar method is to be employed, when we meet a class of students. In order to teach English effectively one can provide masterfully over coursework, a dividing learning experience, skill-based approach, multimedia interactions, interactive exercises, personal evaluation and assessment tools simulations and most importantly a student centric nuts and bolts approach to all complex concepts.

Skill-Based Approach

In line with this utilitarian skill-based approach reading must be complemented by practice in the correct and apt choice and use of words sentences and forms. The era in today's world is facing an overload in technology, that only small minority is able to keep up with the important ability of reading. Students are too busy with their computer games and television and glued on their own computer screen, amazing the wealth of knowledge through internet search engines. And that is a shame because reading offers a productive approach to improve vocabulary and word power. It is advisable to indulge in at least half an hour of reading a day to keep abreast of various styles of writing and new vocabulary. Reading has a long and distinguish track record for establishing positive and lasting benefits to humanity. It is considered one of the best habits that one can inculcate in oneself. Student can be encouraged to be a regular reader. They are bound to come across the words of various authors and will be exposed to several different literary style and thus keep on learning new words phrases, idioms and learn to use them in several different ways as well. Educational researchers have also found a strong correlation between reading and vocabulary knowledge. For writer, reading is essential. Reading a wide range of authors in a wide range of genre is very effective way of helping oneself. All the different style of writing, the

range of voices used and the techniques employed by the published authors will help develop one's own style and voice. Reading requires remembering details, facts and figures and in literature, plot lines, themes and characters. Also, if he/she develops the habit of reading he/she will become more confident and self-assured in abilities to comprehend and understand all type of information. How do the teacher help students to come out of the vicious circle? This is a million-dollar question. How can he or she open the magic doors of the world of reading? Reading is a vital skill and the one who cannot read, or enjoy reading gradually turns into a slow learner, loses interest in studies and becomes a failure in life. Of course, we could make reading compulsory by forcing the student to read will yield no positive results. There is a saying that, one could take the horse to the pond but the horse must feel the thirst to drink. Here are some ways in which we could inculcate the reading habits among the students. It is advisable to indulge in at least half an hour of reading a day to keep abreast of various styles of writing and new vocabulary. Reading has a long and distinguish track record for establishing positive and lasting benefits to humanity. It is considered one of the best habits that one can inculcate in him. The teacher can use specific activities for developing reading, using materials that are authentic. For instance

- 1) Passages from Newspapers, from magazines, tourist guides can be given to the learners and reading activities such as answering questions on the passage or preparing tables of information for giving directions for the tourist may be set.
- 2) Dictionary based activities: pages from a good dictionary can be given to the learners and reading activities such as alphabetizing words or finding out abbreviations.

Student should be encouraged to ask questions in various kinds. Word power is increased by building up associative system of vocabulary. And their extension expansion of general knowledge is brought in to create challenges and to build up their English expression bank and idiom banks are set up in order to increase transactions. students can be exposed to a wide range of written English from magazine, articles, from Cynewulf and Virginia Woolf. Purposeful learning experiences are presented in the forms of a variety of exercises that are intellectually challenging, communicating effectively and socially relevant and useful. The exercise materials are intended to generate not only interaction in the class, but also parallel material, so that is unseen will be remained and seen forever. The confidence of the learners is built up along with their expression.

Personal Evolution and Assessment

Let us now turn our attention to the ways and approaches to assess the students on their speaking skills. The methods used for assessing oral communication skills depend upon the purpose of assessment. There are three important trends:

- 1) The first trend focuses on communicative activities that reflect a variety of settings.
- 2) Secondly on using communication to achieve specific purpose, such as, to inform, to persuade, and to solve problems.
- 3) The third trend focuses on basic competencies needed for everyday life — for example, giving instructions / directions, asking for information, or providing basic information in an emergency situation.

In Order to Assess the Students, the Following Techniques May Be Introduced

- 1) Reading a dialogue or a newspaper would help the teacher to know whether the student reads with a complete understanding.
- 2) Showing video clips and making them to comment on the pictures. Through this the teacher can observe whether the student views the video with critical observation.
- 3) Asking the students to give a short talk on selected topics of routine interests. Through this task the student's ability to organize his thoughts on the topic can be assessed.
- 4) Asking the students to participate in simulated activities would help to assess the student's creative ability.
- 5) Engage the students in seminar presentations and group discussions. These tasks would help to make assessment of non-verbal behaviors of the student.

Can Communication Skills Be Learnt?

It is assumed until recently that students eke with a good communication skills and appropriate attitude by observing and modelling their behaviour and that of their teachers. Good communication can be learnt and improved. It begins with good listening and preparedness to acknowledge the ideas and ethics of others. While at the same time, considering the adaptation of one's own to suit changing circumstances are because, one has been

shown that they are acceptable to others. Listening effectively is more than just hearing the words of others. It involves concentrating or energy, on understanding and interpreting the message with the meaning the center intended. It is not at all necessary to use bombastic words and terms to impress others, rather it is how clearly we express our ideas and how simply we put forward are thoughts, in which the essence of good communication skills lies. The most important point is to make student realise that he/she has the ability to communicate and that use the ability continually while relating to other people. Knowing words is the key to understanding and being understood. The bulk of learning a new language consists of learning new words. Grammatical knowledge does not make for great proficiency in a language. (Vermeer 1992).

Aspects of Word Teaching and Learning

It is generally agreed that knowledge of the word form (pronunciation and spelling), word structure, the common derivations of the word in a phrase and sentence, word meaning (multiplicity of meaning and metaphorical extensions of meaning), lexical relations of the word with other words such as synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, common collocations (Laufer 1997) is essential for an educated native speaker. The second language learners knowledge of the word may be partial. Some areas might be difficult for a second language learner. Here are some of the ways to learn words in an interesting way. A number of games are suggested for improving the reading skills, especially in early classes. A few of them are given below:

Advantage of Language Games

Language games, if organised well with care and interest, help the student to acquire a lot of language, because while playing a game, student have opportunities to learn without stress and anxiety, which is good for learning. These games serve as a valuable input for language acquisition in a tension-free situation.

Kangaroo Words

A female Kangaroo keeps its young ones in its pouch. A kangaroo word is a word which carries within its spelling in the normal order, a smaller word which means exactly the same. For example, the kangaroo word 'illuminated' contains the synonym 'lit' among its letters. 'Evacuate' (Kangaroo Word), contains the synonym 'vacate'. e.g. Amicable(amicable), Appropriate(apt), Salvage (verb) save, Encourage (urge), Observe(see), Destruction (ruin).

Beheadment Words

Removing the first letter of a word is called beheadment. In beheadment, a word loses its first letter and becomes another word. Examples: 'Sparking', beheaded, becomes PARKING. In the seventeenth century, the poet George Herbert included this form of word play in his poem, "Paradise":

I bless thee, Lord, because I GROW
Among thy trees, which in a ROW
To thee both fruit and order OW....

Conclusion

It is evident that language teaching can promote learner autonomy by designing task-based modules and using them either independently in the classroom or uploading them as online class.

Reference

- [1] George Anish. "Amazing English". www.theamazingenglish.com.
- [2] Kajur R.P. "Using English in Classroom", *The Journal of English Language Teaching (India)* XLV/4 2007.
- [3] Laufer Batia. "Whats in Word that Makes it Hard or Easy: Some Internal Factors that Affect the Learning of Words." In Schmitt and MacCarthy eds.(1997) p.140-155.
- [4] Vermeer, A. (1992). Exploring the second language learner lexicon. In L. Verhoeven and J.

UPGRADING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION PRACTICES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENTAL GOALS IN SCHOOL SETTINGS

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Abstract

By 2030, the society should ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles. The teacher should build and upgrade education facilities for disabilities and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive and effective learning environments for all. The paper tries to portray the responsibility of an educator to stand for the cause of protecting the rights of every individual and catering to the needs of special children in protecting their human rights, gender equality and global citizenship. The appreciation of cultural diversity amidst exclusion must contribute to sustainable developmental goals. It's time that governmental agencies as well as mainstream institutions woke up to the reality that segregation of children with challenging needs is morally unjustifiable and a violation of human rights. The right of every child to contribute to economy of the country through building productivity is possible only when teachers realize the goals of the nation to strive for inclusive education.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Sustainable Developmental Goals, School Settings*

Introduction

Inclusive education (IE) is a new approach towards educating the children with disability and learning difficulties with that of normal ones within the same roof. It seeks to address the learning needs of all children with a specific focus on those who are vulnerable to marginalization and exclusion. It implies all learners – with or without disabilities being able to learn together through access to common pre-school provisions, schools and community educational setting with an appropriate network of support services. This is possible only in flexible education system that assimilates the needs of diverse range of learners and adapts itself to meet these needs. The sustainable developmental goals (SDG4) as per National Education policy 2020 are put in a nutshell as:

- 1) Ensuring lifelong learning opportunities for all, from early childhood to adult education;
- 2) Ensuring equity, inclusion and gender equality;
- 3) Ensuring effective learning and the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills and competencies;
- 4) Ensuring the relevance of learning, in terms of vocational and technical skills for decent work as well as for global citizenship in a plural and interconnected world.

Inclusive Sustainability

Inclusive sustainability works to draw genuine connections between environmental sustainability and social justice. This new concept challenges traditional environmental practices that ignore or overlook important social justice issues. Inclusive sustainability directly engages students and increases student success. Inclusive education resonates positively with widely agreed values of creating *sustainable futures* by emphasizing the value of each individual, embracing education for all, and promoting *sustainable wellbeing* in communities. Our point of view is that researching inclusive education may support the building of resilient and tolerant communities in our current pluralistic world and enhance equality and equity in educational settings. New educators can develop their practice to respond to the inclusion challenges they are facing in practice. For experienced educators, the shift to the idea of lifelong learning within the teaching profession has become increasingly popular. It is noted that educators particularly feel ill equipped to work inclusively with pupils with social, emotional and behavioural issues.

Strategies to Promote Inclusion in Today's Classroom

The strategies for promoting inclusive education in the classroom is the application of diverse pedagogical approaches such as collaborative learning, team building, discussions, project method, to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product etc. Inclusive education represents universal values of social justice and incorporates the idea of constantly evolving democracy. Role play: Role-play is an important example of collaborative learning which uses drama techniques to teach facts and values and stimulate critical thinking in a safe environment. Roleplay can, therefore, be described as a teaching-learning activity that embodies many of the ideas of inclusive education and sustainable development. Collaborative learning: Learners from diverse and inclusive backgrounds can collaborate together to study, share and discuss recent trends in learning. Diversity-rich

classrooms and collaborative learning methods, like role play, are inclusive strategies that may be useful in classroom education. Applying the principles of inclusive education may be a relevant approach in education. Two strategies commonly used to make inclusive education visible in higher education are through policies (e.g., widening participation) and diverse pedagogical approaches. Widening participation involves concerted efforts to increase student enrolment from underrepresented population subgroups. Effective teacher training in special education: In the successful implementation of inclusive practices, generalist teachers are seen as having an important role. This does not exclude the support received from special education teachers when needed. The regular school teachers are core actors in developing inclusive practices and they need to learn to meet the needs of a diverse range of learners effectively, including those with special educational needs and disabilities. This has major implications in the sense of preparation of all teachers in this direction and higher education institutions delivering teacher education programs are seen as being responsible for this aspect. The importance of teacher education for the development of inclusive educational systems cannot be contested. Therefore, teacher education programs are expected to equip future teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to teach diverse student populations and meet the diverse needs of different categories of learners. Support of family: The integration of the family in educating their children allows for the optimization of educational intervention. Inclusive education has had its origins in special education, which has been conceptually overtaken. The development of an inclusive and quality education necessarily requires the real and effective participation of the family and other social agents in the education of children and young people. Professional training: Many options for professional learning offer for qualified educators seeking additional qualifications tend to emphasise individual knowledge and the development of skills to work with students with specific educational needs—e.g., autism, dyslexia, or behavioural issues.

Challenges in Promoting Inclusive Education

Quality Education seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. The challenge is how do we expound on these efforts to use technology to forward quality education for all that is inclusive more rapidly to meet SDG 4 by 2030. there is lack of access to education infrastructures, there are not enough ability for those developing nations to have the same level or better yet the same accessibilities to receive education. Many young people from marginalised groups are vulnerable within education systems. The inherent complexity of modern society tends to exclude many young people rather than include them resulting in an increased risk of many young people dropping out of educational provision. It is acknowledged that early school leaving and failing to opt into other forms of educational provision can have a long-term impact. This impact has consequences for both the individual and society. Indeed, studies suggest that few educators believe themselves to be prepared to deal with challenging behaviour, which is of interest as such behavioural challenges are often said to cause the failure of inclusive programmes. If educators are not supported to provide effective learning opportunities for all young people, this can impact both the young person's career prospects and their health and wellbeing, and often results in poverty and poor health outcomes in the long term. This in turn can have a detrimental economic impact on countries and negatively impact on social cohesion within and between communities. If educators themselves believe that this approach is not possible then it may make them hesitant about working with particular groups or learners until they have received specialist training. The idea that educators need more training can also enter public consciousness and become understood as the main barrier to inclusion in schools. Despite its relevance, there is not much research aimed at collecting the voice of the families of students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) about their relationship with the school system. Attention to the most vulnerable students must be a priority for the education system and today's society. Furthermore, to assess whether and to what extent such real and effective participation occurs, reliable and valid measuring instruments are needed. These instruments would make it possible not only to evaluate the situation at a given time but also the possible change it may have undergone due to an intervention program.

Some of the Other Issues Facing Inclusive Education are:

- 1) Lack of training among the teachers
- 2) Lack of teaching competencies in handling special children
- 3) Lack of infrastructure facilities
- 4) Less student involvement
- 5) Methods of teaching disabilities
- 6) retention of special needs children in schools
- 7) Social attitude towards disabilities

- 8) Unable to understand special children needs
- 9) Parental attitude towards disabilities
- 10) Unable to link learning and practice
- 11) Lack of policy implementation

There are several obstacles and challenges related to educational system which hinders to promote inclusive education. It is not impossible to attain success in inclusive education in nation through effective strategies and other means. To make inclusion appropriate teacher preparation, awareness and attitude towards disabilities, retention of special children etc. must be made compulsory in all programmes irrespective of elementary, secondary level and higher education.

Assessment of Inclusive Practices to Enable Sustainability

A valuable method for determining the quality of inclusion within schools is to ascertain the experiences of the parents of children with disabilities, and it is necessary to have reliable and valid measuring instruments for this purpose. It is necessary to rethink how the families of students with SEN participate in educational centers, by promoting more collaborative formulas where each one can develop his or her role, joining all efforts in favor of inclusive and high-quality education, and shortening the distance between the participation model established in educational legislation and what is actually happening. Achieving these ambitious and necessary goals is not possible if there are no instruments to assess families' perspectives on these aspects. Ensuring that standards targeted are achieved through testing students, policies achieved or not, barriers to inclusion in terms of structural facilities, instructional materials, assistive devices and strategies are implemented or not.

Final Thoughts

The advancements of ICTs have created numerous opportunities for improving education, especially for persons with disabilities. In my view, investing in inclusive education is ultimately an investment in a better future for everyone and should be a top priority. education should be provided regardless of any of the barriers and challenges that people with disabilities may have. Henceforth, inclusive education is not only for children but also for those who are hoping to access education but cannot because of a physical or social or any type of barrier. Therefore, technology may enable for a platform that gives access to the virtual learning. Persons with disabilities should have the equal opportunity from the stages before, during and after receiving education—for employment and other social activities. Only these initiatives start from education and educational empowerment is possible only when children with special needs contribute to the productive labour and economic development of the country.

References

- [1] Adams, M.E.; Bell, L.A.E.; Griffin, P.E. Teaching for Diversity and Social Justice, 2nd ed.; Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group: Abingdon/Oxford, UK, 2007.
- [2] Alur, M. (2002). Education and Children with Special Needs: from Segregation to Inclusion, New Delhi: Sage Publications
- [3] Antil, N. (2014), Inclusive Education: Challenges and Prospects in India, IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science, Volume 19, Issue 9, PP 85-89 e-ISSN: 2279-0837, p-ISSN: 2279- 0845. www.iosrjournals.org
- [4] Avramidis, E.; Norwich, B. Teachers' attitudes towards integration/inclusion: A review of the literature. Eur. J. Spec. Needs Educ. 2002, 17, 129–147.
- [5] Essays, UK. (November 2013). The Importance And Definition Of Inclusion Education Essay. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/education/the-importance-and-definition-of-inclusion-education-essay.php?cref=1>
- [6] Florian, L. Conceptualising Inclusive Pedagogy: The Inclusive Pedagogical Approach in Action. In Inclusive Pedagogy Across the Curriculum (International Perspectives on Inclusive Education, Vol. 7); Emerald Group Publishing Limited: Bingley, UK, 2015; pp. 11–24.
- [7] Florian, L.; Camedda, D. Enhancing Teacher Education for Inclusion. Eur. J. Teach. Educ. 2020, 43, 4–8.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS ON MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

The globalized world requires a greater percentage of work force of qualified teachers for promoting multicultural education in a diverse environment. The spectrum of education has been expanding across the boundaries to promote inclusion and ethnic differences. The concept of multicultural education is attuned to develop the intellectual needs of the diverse students and inculcate cultural integration to foster a sense of integrity among the diverse groups of the global society. Therefore, the paper aims to broaden the perspectives of teachers towards multicultural education in the 21st century. The concept of multiculturalism nurtures educational equality among the student community and it is the duty of the training faculty to flourish the aspect of multiculturalism for generations to prosper.

Keywords: *Perception, Multicultural education, Teachers*

Introduction

The culture of our society is a greater asset to our country, preserving and transmitting the traditions of our country among the students balancing social constraints. Today many contemporary countries are characterized by multiculturalism, multilingualism and different ethnic views. Encouraging multiculturalism in schools can be stimulated by conducting special programs. The program is realized through a variety of methods: press, publishing newspapers, encouraging panel discussions, oral reports, dramatizations, role playing, and so on. Multiculturalism is not achieved only in schools, but also in family upbringing, by powerful and influential means, mass-media, books, movies and a complete social environment. The purpose of multicultural education should be a person with broad views and broad multicultural orientation, someone who can give meaning to individual national and cultural identity, and someone who will appreciate other peoples' cultural varieties and their achievements. Multicultural education involves more than reading a book about a historical character of color or celebrating a holiday surrounding a diverse hero. It includes policies, practices, and pedagogical approaches that affirm students' differences and intersectionality.

Literature Review

Multicultural education is the need of the hour. In a secular nation like India, multicultural curriculum is much needed in terms of cultural mutual respect, goodwill, preservation, nurture and transition of culture. Multicultural curriculum, multicultural learning teaching methods, equality in classroom teaching, school democratic environment, equality of opportunity, creation of mutual cultural tolerance are essential for the future education system and indeed for the development of the country. "It helps all students acquire the knowledge, skills, attributes, and attitudes needed to function in a democratic society while feeling valued and heard," Howell said. As established earlier, multicultural education grew out of the ethnic studies movement which was a part of the civil rights movement, multicultural education arose from the western democratic ideals of freedom, justice and equality (Banks, 1993b). It refers to the cultural diversities that come from the existence of two or more groups in a society where people's views and practices generate a characteristic sense of a collective identity. multiculturalism admits and recognizes the importance of beliefs, convictions, values and the different ways of life. It prompts self-understanding and encourages the sense of someone's belonging somewhere as an individual or in groups with similar opinions.

Incorporating Multiculturalism in the Classroom

Teachers should question their expectations for students of different identities and reflect on how those expectations affect how they engage in the pedagogy. The following are the strategies for the teachers. Multicultural teachers and education create a moral and engaged community through opportunities for learners from diverse ethnic groups to have a wider perspective of the world. However, problems related to cultural diversity are still occurring nowadays and are much more complex and problematic than decades ago. Hence, multicultural education is more crucial than ever in breaking down stereotypes, intolerance, and bullying within schools; ensuring our new citizens feel welcome and included in their newly adoptive society.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Developing critical thinking among educators: The growing emphasis on multicultural education is aligned with a broader trend in education that seeks to make schools more inclusive. That means inclusion for students from various cultures, students with disabilities, and more. Teachers who want to ensure all of their students feel welcome and accepted in the classroom may want to look into ways to incorporate multicultural perspectives effectively and respectfully. Multicultural education is sometimes combined with other teaching strategies like social and emotional learning that also focus on students' well-being and individuality.

Developing a culture of mutual respect: It attempts to solve the problem of language and racial discrimination among the students. The introduction of new cultural groups created a number of issues in the education space. Historically, language barriers were a huge problem everywhere in most Western countries – as public education put heavy emphasis on teaching English and assimilation into the adoptive culture, which negatively impacted new immigrants.

Knowledge of ethnicities among Teachers to avoid exclusion and marginalization: Certain cultural groups are being underrepresented in school curriculum and textbooks, and this issue was observed across secondary and tertiary education (Banks 2013 *The Construction and Historical Development of Multicultural Education, 1962–2012*). Contents of their textbooks are perceived to be irrelevant to them, there is minimal material for them to relate to culturally. This may be a challenge for them to study as everything they have learnt is so foreign to their cultural background, language or lifestyle. Ethnic minorities could not relate to what they are learning in school, and, hence, these students feel “unwelcome, insignificant and alienated” (Gay, 2004). Such irrelevant content in school may make it extremely difficult for them to adapt to their new society in which they find themselves living.

Learn accurate representations of cultural groups: Knowledge that the teacher teaches in schools should be more neutral and objective so that students can receive correct information on cultural groups (by people of that culture) that they are not familiar with. Some students may not be fully familiar with their own cultural group as well, such as students who grew up in one place but have different ethnic backgrounds. The teacher should not misinterpret their culture without being fully aware of their cultural traditions.

Promote Harmony and integration in a school setting: Multicultural education acts as a way for students from different cultural groups to communicate and interact with each other. Students may distance themselves from other cultural groups because they do not know them well; they may not understand the background, histories, belief systems, or where differences and similarities exist. In this context, there is a strong likelihood of ‘othering’ – creating an ‘us and them’ mentality – as the groups tend to keep unto themselves. Promoting multicultural education may clear up some of the misconceptions students have towards certain cultural groups and eradicate the stigma they put on these groups. They can incorporate group projects or discussions in class when teaching topics on multiculturalism. This allows students to step out of their comfort zone and communicate with each other; inviting the culturally diverse students to speak of their festivities, music, food, and belief systems.

Promoting Equity and capacity building in culturally diverse groups: Students are all unique individuals, treating everyone equally does not mean that students’ needs are being addressed adequately. Culturally diverse students have their own set of challenges in a given school environment. In order to help these students overcome these challenges, it is not enough to give all students equal opportunities but, more importantly, teachers provide specific help to have better academic achievements

Decipher Cultural biases: Everyone in the world is raised with their own cultural beliefs and practices. For some people, those cultural practices are shared by most people in their community. In those cases, it can be hard to notice cultural assumptions and biases because they seem normal. For people of marginalized cultures, it is often noticeable when their own beliefs and practices are out of step with the majority. Teachers who want to create a truly multicultural classroom can begin by identifying and deconstructing their own cultural biases. That means taking a step back and examining beliefs, assumptions, and practices that make up the fabric of everyday life. For example, it might not be a good idea to throw a pizza party during Ramadan if a class has Muslim students, as they will be unable to participate if they are fasting during the day. Researching and reading about other cultures and diverse experiences is a way to start deconstructing these biases, but the process is ongoing without a set end.

Challenges in Multiculturalism

If teachers are unable to handle diversity in the classroom it will enhance the marginalization of the various cultures leading to exclusion of the minority community. Educators from dominant groups think the key issues and best solutions are not necessarily the same as what students, parents, and community members from non-dominant groups think. Some of the most difficult but most necessary work in multicultural education

involves helping those who are used to being in charge learn to listen to and take seriously those they have learned to dismiss. Teachers are responsible for sharing knowledge with their students. The way for teachers to effectively teach their students is through gaining accurate knowledge on multiculturalism. Accordingly, teachers should be highly aware that there are individual differences in the classroom (Basbay, 2014); teaching plans and personal teaching styles may need to vary to cater to different cultural groups.

Ways to Overcome Barriers in Implementing Multiculturalism

In an everchanging global scenario it has become imperative to equip students with adequate knowledge on multiculturalism and multilingualism. In India, a culturally rich and more diverse society utmost importance is given to diversity and social awareness on cultural traditions of diverse groups. To better facilitate multicultural education in a school setting, it is salient for school authorities and faculty members to know how culturally diverse that school is. It would be extremely difficult to offer help to different cultural groups in school without identifying what groups there are within their school community. Technology is a useful tool to bridge these groups together and provide cultural-related knowledge. It is through the school itself to set an example of being proactive in multicultural education, demonstrating to their students the importance of multiculturalism and multicultural education. Most importantly, schools are, in many ways, a microcosm of the multicultural society of the US. Students and teachers benefit from being able to express their own cultural values in a safe environment. They also benefit from learning about other cultures respectfully, without alienating or bullying their peers. Diversity in the classroom can be an added advantage that helps make the school environment richer and more reflective of the real world. Multicultural education must be handled respectfully, and this can take practice. Fortunately, there are many steps that teachers and students can take to improve their cultural understanding.

Concluding Thoughts

Teachers can help students feel seen and represented by giving them access to diverse literature. When students can read about others who share some of their cultural experiences, they may feel more welcome and comfortable in the classroom than if they can only read about the dominant cultural narrative. Teachers can have some of these books available in the classroom and speak to the school librarian about expanding the collection if possible. Teachers must avoid putting students on the spot or requiring them to speak about their culture if they are not enthusiastic about the prospect. It can be challenging for students to be part of a cultural minority at school, and although it can benefit all students to learn about other cultures, students should not be required to take on the burden of educating all those around them. Teachers should be aware that personal assignments like these can be challenging for some students. Students in foster care, students who are refugees and might have lost family heirlooms, or any other possibilities, may struggle with and feel alienated by these assignments. Teachers should make sure to have an appropriate alternative for any students who do not feel comfortable speaking about their own lives and families. When teachers understand where these students are coming from, they can help them adjust to a new system without punishing them for having a different approach to learning. A school is a place of learning, but learning can go beyond what is in a textbook. Hence teacher should respect the cultural differences among the students and develop strategies to expand the horizons of learning to inclusion and marginalization.

References

- [1] Aktoprak, A.; Yigit, P.; Güneyli, A. Attitudes of primary school teachers toward multicultural education. *Qual. Quant.* 2017, 52, 181–194.
- [2] Gay, G. The Importance of Multicultural Education. *Educ. Leadersh.* 2004, 61, 30–35.
- [3] Goldsberg, D. T. (1994): *Multikulturalism*, Basil Blackwell, USA.
- [4] Holm, G.; Zilliacus, H. Multicultural education and intercultural education: Is there a difference? In *Dialogs on Diversity and Global Education*; Talib, M., Loima, J., Paavola, H., Patrikainen, S., Eds.; Peter Lang: New York, NY, USA, 2009; pp. 11–28.
- [5] Johnson, J.R.; McIntosh, A.S. Toward a Cultural Perspective and Understanding of the Disability and Deaf Experience in Special and Multicultural Education. *Remedial Spec. Educ.* 2008, 30, 67–83.

PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS TOWARDS INTEGRATION OF ART EDUCATION AMONG SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Integrating art education among school students will enhance their skills and creative knowledge which helps them to concentrate more on their studies. This paper explores the significance of art education and how important it is for school students to develop their creative skills during their studies. Implications from the review of studies suggest the need for the availability of training, adapted curriculum, positive attitude towards the integration of art education, and utmost responsibility of teachers. Under the quantitative survey design, 80 teachers from a government and private school teachers participated in the study and responded to a Likert questionnaire measuring attitudes toward the integration of art education among school students. The results were analyzed using the IBM SPSS package for independent t-test, and the statistical significance was found by t-test with respect to the type of management, qualification, and years of experience. Based on these results we can conclude saying that there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to the type of management. There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers towards the Integration of art education among school students with respect to their educational qualifications and, years of experience. Compared to teachers of government and teachers of private were equally involved in the integration of art education among school students. Lack of time, funding, and unavailability of study leaves were major barriers that affected the integration of art education in schools. Based on this study's findings, it is suggested that the integration of art education in schools may be taken as an ongoing process.

Keywords: *Art Integration, Perception Of Teachers.*

Introduction

Arts integration helps teachers rethink the roles they play and their relationships with students. Teachers are seeking effective teaching strategies to support an array of student learning needs. The arts hold the potential to transform the learning experience for students. However, the use of art integration is limited and unknown to many educators. The problem that prompted this study is the need for teachers to effectively teach each student in a method that not only meets the individual needs but pushes students to perform at higher levels of academic achievement. Art education programs, no doubt because the arts are considered tangential to skills that lead to basic employment, have been labeled unnecessary for the development of academic achievement (Eisner, 1998). A key assumption held by some educators regarding the continuance of arts education in schools has influenced the topic of this study. The concept of arts integration is to incorporate connections to content while relating to the real world. If educators are to compete in a global economy, children deserve every advantage including the arts. Implementing an integrated arts curriculum is both exciting and intimidating to teachers. This study is an attempt to know the perception of teachers towards the integration of art education among school teachers.

Significance of the Study

The NEP 2020 stated in page 12 (para 4.7) that: "Art-integration is a cross-curricular pedagogical approach that utilizes various aspects and forms of art and culture as the basis for learning of concepts across subjects. As a part of the thrust on experiential learning, art-integrated education will be embedded in classroom transactions not only for creating joyful classrooms, but also for imbuing the Indian ethos through integration of Indian art and culture in the teaching and learning process at every level. This art-integrated approach will strengthen the linkages between education and culture." Keeping the latest National Education Policy 2020 into consideration, recommendations, commissions and values suggested by different schools of philosophy in promoting art education into teaching, it is relevant that the need of the day is to fuse art education to bring life into teaching to make teaching learning process effective and joyful by enriched strategies. Teachers have the capacity to train the children based on their own interests and understanding, rather than teaching methods they don't understand. The process of learning an art brings with it 21st-century skills of collaboration, resilience, communication etc. Art promotes freedom of creative expression, which helps students relax and think differently.

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Objectives of the Study

- 1) To study the perception of teachers towards integration of art education among school students with respect to the type of management of the school.
- 2) To compare the perception of teachers in the integration of art education among school students with respect to their educational qualification (UG/PG).
- 3) To compare the perception of teachers in the integration of art education among school students with respect to their years of experience of teaching (>5 years or <5 years of experience).

Research Questions

- 1) What is the perception of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students?
- 2) Will the type of management of schools aid in the integration of art education among school students?
- 3) Will the years of teaching experience of teachers facilitate the integration of art education among school students?
- 4) Will the educational qualification of teachers help in the integration of art education among school students?

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) **H1:** There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to the type of management of schools.
- 2) **H2:** There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to their educational qualification UG/PG.
- 3) **H3:** There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to their teaching experience (more than 5 years and less than 5 years).

Variables of the Study

Dependent variable - perception of teachers towards integration of art education among school students. Independent variable - Type of school management – Government or Private school Educational qualification of teachers (under-graduation and post-graduation). Years of experience of the teachers (> 5 years or < 5 years of experience).

Methodology

The present study has employed a survey method. Here the researcher has prepared a self-constructed questionnaire consisting of 30 questions (standardized through a pilot study) as a tool to gather the appropriate information from the desired population. Sample: 80 teachers from government and private schools have been selected as the sample of the study. Tool: A questionnaire consisting of 30 questions related to the usefulness of Art Education, Art has a creative expression and Enhancement of students' personalities on the integration of Art Education among school students. Closed-ended questions to access the quality and possible use for integration of art education in schools, for positive impact were prepared for study. It is viable to suggest the present study based on the focussed group discussion as one the important tool in carrying out this study so that more inputs can be gained from the teachers. Statistical techniques: As per the requirement of the study suitable statistical techniques are applied which include: independent t-test, standard deviation, mean, etc., by using the SPSS package on excel. After the data is statistically analyzed then the data is interpreted. The findings and conclusions are written based on the interpreted data.

Analysis of the Data

H1- There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to the type of management of schools.

Table 4.1: The variation in the perceptions of school teachers with respect to the type of management.

VARIABLE	N	MEAN	SD	t-value	Df	Level of significance
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GOVT	40	122.75	9.242	0.414	78	0.05
PRIVATE	40	121.85	10.182			

Significant at 0.05 level of significance Table value = 1.664

From the above table the mean score of government school teachers is 122.75 is greater than the mean score of private school teachers means score i.e., 121.85. The standard deviation of private school teachers is SD=10.182 is greater than the standard deviation of government school teachers SD=9.242. The t -value =0.414 at 78 df is less than the table value=1.664. Hence null hypothesis is accepted and the research hypothesis is rejected. Hence from the above data, we can conclude that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to the type of school management.

H2: There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to their educational qualification UG/PG.

Table 4.2: The variation in the perceptions of school teachers with respect to their educational qualifications.

VARIABLE	N	MEAN	SD	t-value	Df	Level of significance
PG	36	125.81	9.951	3.086	78	0.05
UG	44	119.43	8.519			

Significant at 0.05 level of significance Table value = 1.664

From the above table, the mean score of the post-graduate (PG) teachers is 125.81 is greater than the mean score of undergraduate (UG) teachers mean score is 119.43. The standard deviation of post-graduate (PG) teachers is SD=9.951 is greater than the standard deviation of undergraduate (UG) teachers SD=8.519. The t -value =3.086 at 78 df is greater than the table value=1.664. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

Hence from the above data, we can conclude that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to their educational qualifications.

H3: There is a significant difference in the perception of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to their teaching experience (more than 5 years and less than 5 years).

Table 4.3: The variation in the perceptions of school teachers with respect to their years of experience.

VARIABLE	N	MEAN	SD	t-value	Df	Level of significance
>5 years	45	124.33	10.462	2.182	78	0.05
<5 years	35	119.69	7.951			

Significant at 0.05 level of significance Table value = 1.664

From the above table, the mean score of those with >5 years of experience teachers is 124.33 is greater than the mean score of those with <5 years of experience teachers' mean score is 119.69. The standard deviation of the >5 years of experience teachers is SD=10.462 is greater than the standard deviation of the <5 years of experience teachers SD=7.951. The t -value =2.182 at 78 df is greater than the table value=1.664. Hence null hypothesis is rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted. Hence from the above data, we can conclude that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to their years of experience.

Findings and Discussions of the Study

The following are the major findings of the study of perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students. Discussion 1: The first finding of the study is there is no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to the type of school management. The independent t-test conducted has proved that the government school teachers and private teachers have significantly the same levels of perceptions on the integration of art education among school students. This may be because nowadays teaching is changing rapidly everyone wants to update themselves by

participating in various professional programs. This finding of my study is supported by the study of Kimberly Lloyd (2017), is discussed the benefits of art education in schools for better understanding of the students. Private and government schools want to excel in their services and want to be the best in the society. Educational professionals (teachers) learning through their careers is essential. Thus, the integration of art education in schools is the same for both private and government teachers. Discussion2: The second finding of the study is there is a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers in integrating art education among school students with respect to their educational qualifications. The independent t-test conducted has proved that there is a significant difference in the perceptions of teachers in integrating art education among school students. From this, we can interpret that the UG and PG teachers have different levels of perception in the integration of art education among school students. Qualification is a bias for integrating art education among school students. Both UG and PG teachers have dissimilar confidence in their ability to participate in art integration programs, this finding of my study is supported by the study of Erin Moody-Zoet, (2014), who carried research on the implementation of teacher art integration among school students and its impact on educational quality, found that to ensure educational quality, countries are forced to carry out art integration programs as a major means of teacher's creative development. Art integration programs have been implemented in schools to update teachers with new knowledge and skills by performing different activities in groups and individually to address teachers' immediate concerns irrespective of their qualification background. Discussion 3: The Third finding of the study is there is a significant difference in the perception of teachers towards integration of art education among school students based on years of teaching experience i.e., >5 years of teaching experience and < 5 years of teaching experience. This may be because teachers with more number years of experience want to enroll themselves in various programs and update themselves with new ways of teaching methodologies strategies and approaches So, that they reach the new generation. This study is supported by the study of Kate Latham, (2017), Integrating Art into the Classroom: A Necessary Component of a Well-Rounded Education, Kate Latham Western Kentucky University. Without art education in the classroom, students would be missing out on important educational benefits. The best outcome for art education would be that every student is introduced to art through a designated classroom with a specialized instructor. It shows that teachers having more number teaching experience (>5 years) want to participate in art integration programs to enrich their ability and creative skills with comparing to less teaching experience (<5 years) teachers. More experienced teachers showed interest in participating in integrating art education in schools emphasizing lifelong learning.

Educational Implications

Accordingly, it is presumed that teachers have to engage themselves in planning and executing their art skills basis to cope-up with the rapidly changing world. In this regard, that teacher development is an essential element to bring meaningful changes in addressing equity, quality, relevance, creativity, and efficiency. The purpose of the study is to understand the positive and negative factors affecting the integration of art education in schools. Since positive factors enable researchers to develop more qualified and enriched skills and negative factors enable researchers to avoid factors having undesired consequences. Therefore, it is important to investigate the integration of art education in schools' needs of teachers, and the needs of teachers for individual creative skills which constitute a basis for the needs analysis. Art education ensures that teachers maintain and enhance the creative knowledge and skills you need in the field. Art education helps teachers to stay interested. Experience is a great teacher, but it does mean that we tend to do what we have done before. Focused art integration in school opens you up to new possibilities, new knowledge, and new skill areas.

Conclusion

This research aimed at exploring teachers' engagement in integrating art education among school students' activities, perceived importance of different art activities, skills to be focused on in future training, and barriers to integration of art education of teachers. A comparison of teachers' opinions was also made by educational qualifications, type of school management, and years of teaching experience. The findings of my study are there is no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers towards the integration of art education among school students with respect to the type of management of the school, but there is a significant difference with respect to their educational qualifications and years of teaching experience i.e., >5 years of teaching experience and < 5 years of teaching experience. This study is significant because it will be added to the scanty empirical knowledge about the status of the integration of art education among school teachers. There was a significant difference in the educational qualifications of teachers' opinions about their involvement in art-integrating activities. School management must encourage and facilitate their teacher's participation in art activities. For

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helping teachers improve their academic and research skills, workshops and seminars must frequently be planned and organized by the school management. To enhance the motivation of teachers, their participation in different formal and informal art education activities must be given adequate weightage in the annual rating and vertical elevation of the school faculty.

Referenes

- [1] Ashley J. Coudriet (2013), A Multiple Case Study Examining Elementary School Art, Music and Physical Education Teachers' Perceptions, Attitudes, and Beliefs Related to Interdisciplinary. B.F.A., University of Massachusetts, 2001 M.S., Central Connecticut State University, 2004 Submitted to the Graduate Faculty of the School of Education in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Education University ofPittsburgh.
- [2] Baker, D. (2013), Art integration and cognitive development. *Journal for Learning through the Arts: A Research Journal on Art Integration in Schools and Communities*. A ResearchJournal on Art Integration in Schools and Communities, 9(1), class_lta_2630. Retrieved from <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/9wv1m987>.
- [3] Bresler, L. (1993), Three orientations to arts in the primary grades: Implications for curriculum reform. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 94(6), 29-34.
- [4] Bresler, L. (1998), —Child art,|| —find art,|| and —art for children||: The shaping of school practice and implications for change. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 100(1).

IMPACT OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES (OER) AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS IN RURAL BACKGROUND IN INDIA

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Abstract

Open Educational Resources (OER) are teaching and learning materials that are either in the public domain or have an open license attached to them (Yekini, Inyang-Udoh, & Doherty, 2016). The goal of this study is to develop a conceptual framework for the design and use of Open Educational Resources (OERs) in teaching and learning methodologies, as well as to determine what impact they can have on students' education. Most of the Open educational resources are progress through E-learning. E-learning is the electronic means by which people communicate and learn, and it has just lately become a crucial source of competitive advantage in the information society. E-Learning, in addition to classroom-based learning, has been suggested to become a new and effective learning technique and environment as information and communication technologies have progressed. (Qi, Liu, & Wang, 2009). This research focused on how open education resources are viewed, how they are used by rural students in India, and the challenges they face when trying to access them.

Keywords: *Impact of OER, Open Access, Open Education, Open Educational Resources*

Introduction

According to Article 26.1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 13.1 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, which affirms "everyone's right to education," everyone has the right to education. (Declaration, p.2012). Open educational materials are a desirable strategy since they provide everyone with an equal opportunity to use them for their educational needs. Education, which was once considered the privilege of the wealthy and elite, is now available to everyone. Many villages with minimal educational knowledge now have numerous schools, but education for a large number of students remains poor. Their poverty reveals the cause for this. Despite their want to learn, the situation does not allow them to do so. For those who wish to learn and want to study, open educational resources are a gift. Open Educational Resources (OERs) have arisen in tandem with developments and advancements in computer and communication technology, making information and knowledge more accessible while also fostering cooperation and collaboration. Through Open Educational Resources (OERs), (Arimoto, 2016) enables an open and flexible learning process that delivers relevant and customized chances for individual requirements. Using technological improvements to benefit educational institutions poses a tremendous challenge, with considerable implications for cost, access, equity, teaching, and quality (Nagaiah, Thanuskodi. 2021). The benefits, challenges, and impact of accessing open educational resources (OER) among Indian college students from rural backgrounds will be examined in this study.

Review of Literature

Singh & Chauhan (2017) aims to gauge the awareness among teacher educators towards Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) on various aspects like conceptual understanding, usability, technological requirements, and present practises and policy guidelines. Since MOOCs are a type of OER that provides a wealth of OER materials to enrolled users freely. A total of 156 responses were received from teachers and educators working in various institutions. The result of the study is that most teachers and educators are aware of essential technical requirements, but many of them are confused about the role of MOOCs in teacher training. Many of them found these MOOCs courses suitable for professional development and awareness programs. There is still a lack of understanding about Indian MOOC initiatives like SWAYAM, NPTEL and other MOOCs platforms. Kumar (2021) studied academic researchers to determine the extent to which Tamil Nadu State University uses OER. To find out how important the use of open education tools and publications are by researchers of open education services and state universities in Tamil Nadu, random sampling techniques have been adopted. An approximate of 300 academic researchers have been selected from Tamil Nadu State University to find out whether there is a significant gap in academic success between male and female. It is found that there is no significant link between open education infrastructure and academic success in Tamil Nadu state universities. OER is a sustainable solution

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to all disasters (earthquakes, wars, floods, rains, recessions, famines, storms, etc.) that affect students' education. Hu, Li, Li, & Huang (2015) conducted study on ZJU students on perceptions of potential barriers to OER use by gender a total of 1,200 students were randomly selected from seven faculties of ZJU to determine the level of OER use. They found that the more students are introduced to OER at school, the more likely they are to use OER. However, OER are often used as supplemental learning resources and have not become part of the formal curriculum in Chinese higher education. That has not changed in India yet. To expand the impact of OER and effectively advance quality education reform in higher education, universities should implement special programmes to introduce OER to their students. As other developing countries want to use OER resources, the findings of this study will greatly benefit future studies of OER.

Objectives

- 1) To find the availability of ICT tools for students in rural areas.
- 2) To identify the purpose of using ICT tools as academic and Entertainment
- 3) To analyze the frequency of using OER.
- 4) To identify the challenges for using OER.
- 5) To investigate the purpose of using open educational resources (OER) by students in rural areas.
- 6) To find out the benefits of using open educational resources on rural area college students.

Hypothesis

- 1) There is no significant difference between male and female to having ICT tools
- 2) There is no significant difference in the frequency with which college students using OER between male and female.
- 3) There is no significant difference between male and female using OER.

Methodology

The target respondents of the study are students from rural area. Samples were collected from students of various arts and science colleges in Pudukkottai region of Tamil Nadu, India. Because Pudukkottai district have more than 42 villages, this rural background students were selected for this study. Before the question paper was given to the students they were explained about the open educational resources and then distributed, a total of 120 students were selected and given the questionnaire and 112 students completed the survey. Data were evaluated using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, frequencies and percentages. Data were coded and analyzed using SPSS version .26.

Table 1: Age * Gender * Frequency of using OER Cross tabulation

Frequency of using OER * Gender * Age Cross tabulation		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Age Below 18	Daily	1	6	7
	Weekly	1	3	4
	Weekly twice	1	2	3
Total		3	11	14
Age 19-21	Daily	6	14	20
	Weekly	14	31	45
	Weekly twice	1	16	17
	Once a month	5	4	9
Total		26	65	91
Age 22- 24	Weekly	3	2	5
	Weekly twice	1	1	2
Total		4	3	7
Frequency of using OER	Daily	7	20	27
	Weekly	18	36	54
	Weekly twice	3	19	22

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	Once a month	5	4	9
Grand Total		33	79	112

Table: 1 gives brief details of the frequency of using OER. The cross table of Age and Gender shows the frequency of using OER: 11 (9.8%) Females and 3 (2.7%) males are using OER an age of below 18, 65(58%) Females and 26 (23.2 %) Male are using OER at the age of 19 to 21, 3 (2.7%) Females and 4 (3.6%) males are using OER at the age of 22 to 24. Frequency of using OER is 20 (17.9%) Female and 7 (6.3%) Male candidates were using daily, 36(32.1%) Female, and 18 (16.1%) Male candidates were using weekly, 19 (17%) Female, and 3 (2.7%) Males were using weekly twice, 4 (3.6%) Female, and 5(4.5%) Male candidates are using OER Once a month. For N=112, the total number of females is 79 (70.5%) and the total number of males is 33 (29.5%).

H: 1 - There is no significant relationship between male and female to having ICT tools

Table 2: Independent sample t-test for significant difference between Male and Female having Information and Communication Technology (ICT) devices

S.no	ICT devices	gender	N	user	%	Mean	t	Sig	Null Hypothesis
1)	Computer	Male	33	10	26.8%	.28	.633	.528	Accepted
		Female	79	20					
2)	Kindle	Male	33	1	9.8%	.10	-1.525	.130	Accepted
		Female	79	10					
3)	Laptop	Male	33	23	83%	.84	-2194	.030	Rejected
		Female	79	70					
4)	Mobile	Male	33	32	94.6%	.96	1.457	.148	Accepted
		Female	79	74					
5)	Tablet	Male	33	3	9.8%	.11	-119	.906	Accepted
		Female	79	8					

The estimated significance value for factors 1,2,4,5 is higher than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, showing there is no significant difference in Male and Female between Using ICT devices, viz., Computer, Kindle, Mobile, and Tablet. For the other factor 3 the estimated significance value is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing there is a significant difference among Male and Female Using ICT devices, viz., Laptop. The most common ICT device used, as shown in Table 2, is a mobile phone (94.6%), followed by a laptop (83%) and computer (26.8 percent) 9.8% of people use tablets and Kindles, respectively.

Fig 1: Male and Female using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) devices

The details of using ICT equipment are shown in Table 2 and Figure 1. Mobile is the most popular choice for this table and figure. This gadget is used by 94.6 percent of people, and it is followed by Laptop. This device is used by 83 percent of individuals, followed by computer users (26.7%), and the least used device is kindly and tablet, which have the same amount of users (9.8%).

Table 3: Purpose of using ICT devices

S.No	Digital Devices	Academic Purpose						Entertainment Purpose					
		M		F		Total		M		F		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%

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1.	Desktop computer	11	17.9	20	17.9	31	27.7	4	3.6	3	2.7	7	6.3
2.	Laptop	20	17.9	65	58.0	85	75.9	24	21.4	50	44.6	74	66.1
3.	Kindle (e-reader)	0	0.0	3	2.7	3	2.7	0	0.0	3	2.7	3	2.7
4.	Smartphone	29	25.9	59	52.7	88	78.6	31	27.7	63	56.3	94	83.9
5.	Tablet/ palmtop	0	0.0	3	2.7	3	2.7	0	1.8	3	2.7	3	4.5

Fig 2: Purpose of using ICT devices

Table 3 and Figure 2 detail how to use ICT devices for academic and recreational purposes. 11 males and 20 females are using desktop computers for academic purposes and 4 males and 3 females are using desktops for entertainment purposes. 20 males and 65 females are using laptops for academic purposes. 24 males and 50 females are using laptops for entertainment. This is the second highest for use. For academic purposes, 29 males and 59 females are using smart phones for academic purposes, and 31 males and 63 females are using them for entertainment purposes. This is the highest value in this table, and only 3 females and no male candidates are using e-readers and tablets for academic and entertainment purposes.

H: 2 - There is no significant difference in the frequency with which college students using OER between male and female

Table 4: Chi-square test for significant difference between Male and Female Frequency of using OER

Sl. No	Frequency of using OER	Male	Female	Total user	%	X ²	df	Sig	Null hypothesis
1	Daily	7	20	27	24.1%	6.152 ^a	3	.104	Accepted
2	Weekly	18	36	54	48.2%				
3	Weekly twice	3	19	22	19.6%				
4	Once a month	5	4	9	8%				
5	Total	33	79	112	100%				

Table 4 indicates the frequency of using open educational resources. The high number of people who utilise OER on a weekly basis is 54 (48.2%). The second group consists of 27 (24.1 %) daily users, while the third group consists of 22 (19.6%) weekly users. There are only 9 users who use OER once a month, and the esteem significant value is greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference between male and female users of OER.

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Table 5: The challenges for using OER
[1- Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neutral, 4- Agree, 5- Strongly Agree.]

S. No	Challenges	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D
1	Lack of technical skills to use OER	16	27	31	27	11	2.91	3.00	3	1.205
		14.3 %	24.1 %	27.7 %	24.1 %	9.8 %				
2	I don't have time to search for and use appropriate resources.	7	27	41	29	8	3.04	3.00	3	1.022
		6.3 %	24.1 %	36.6 %	25.9 %	7.1 %				
3	Hardware and software are in limited supply.	7	21	38	31	15	3.21	3.00	3	1.099
		6.3 %	18.8 %	33.9 %	27.7 %	13.4 %				
4	In my institution, there is a lack of proper Internet access and connectivity.	4	22	34	32	20	3.38	3.00	3	1.100
		3.6 %	19.6 %	30.4 %	28.6 %	17.9 %				
5	There are few OERs in my subject that are relevant to my local context.	7	22	41	30	12	3.16	3.00	3	1.062
		6.3 %	19.6 %	36.6 %	26.8 %	10.7 %				
6	There is a lack of proper OER training.	4	25	31	36	16	3.31	3.00	4	1.082
		3.6 %	22.3 %	27.7 %	32.1 %	14.3 %				
7	Some resources are incomprehensible due to differences in language	9	14	34	34	21	3.39	3.00	4 ^a	1.165
		8.0 %	12.5 %	30.4 %	30.4 %	18.8 %				

^a There are two mode values in factor 7 the highest value is shown

Table 5 shows the Obstacles for using OER in detail. The choices are as follows: The following values are measured on the Likert scale: The five options are: 1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, and 5-Strongly agree. The first is a lack of technical abilities to use OER, which has a Mode value of 3, and the second is a lack of time to find and use relevant resources, which has a Mode value of 3. The third, which has a mode value of 3, indicates that hardware and software are in short supply. The fourth point is there is a shortage of proper Internet access and connectivity in my institution, which has a mean value of 3. , The fifth is the There are few OERs in my subject that are relevant to my local context, which has a mode value of 3, and the sixth opinion is that there is a lack of proper OER training, which has a mode value of 4, and the last opinion is that some resources are incomprehensible due to language differences, which has two mode values of 3 and 4. All of the criteria in this table illustrate that students face some challenges when it comes to using open educational resources.

H: 3 -There is no significant difference between male and female using OER

Table 6: Independent sample t-test for significant difference between Male and Female Purpose of using Open Educational Resources

[1-Never, 2-Rarely, 3-Occasionally, 4-Often, 5-Very Regularly]

S. No	Purpose	1	2	3	4	5	Gender	Mean	Mode	t	Sig.
1.	Access Relevant learning materials	14	18	37	29	14	M	3.30	3	1.177	.242
		12.5	16.1	33	25.9	12.5	F	3.01			
2.	To keep track of notes.	9	31	28	37	7	M	3.27	4	1.610	.110
		8	27.7	25	33	6.3	F	2.91			

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3.	Aware of current facts and figures	8	27	33	19	25	M	3.55	3	1.737	.085
		7.1	24.1	29.5	17	22.3	F	3.10			
4.	To stay current on my subject	7	25	27	41	12	M	3.55	4	1.961	.052
		6.3	22.3	24.1	36.6	10.7	F	3.10			
5.	Aware of technical developments	6	31	28	31	16	M	3.45	4 ^a	1.656	.100
		5.4	27.7	25	27.7	14.3	F	3.06			
6.	I use online learning materials to help me.	9	16	32	42	13	M	3.58	4	1.698	.092
		8	14.3	28.6	37.5	11.6	F	3.19			
7.	To make personal learning easier	11	25	30	27	19	M	3.30	3	.787	.433
		9.8	22.3	26.8	24.7	17	F	3.10			
8.	To learn about topics outside of my major	10	20	29	38	15	M	3.42	4	1.022	.309
		8.9	17.9	25.9	33.9	13.4	F	3.18			
9..	To view online videos of teaching	6	18	34	29	25	M	3.55	3	.634	.527
		5.4	16.1	30.4	25.9	22.3	F	3.39			
10.	To gain access to free learning resources	24	25	20	30	13	M	3.52	4	3.570	.001
		21.4	22.3	17.9	26.8	11.6	F	2.57			

^a There are two mode values in factor 5 the highest value is shown.

The estimated significance value for factors 1 to 9 is higher than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, showing there is no significant difference in gender between the purposes of using Open Educational Resources (OER), viz Access Relevant learning materials, To keep track of notes, aware of current facts and figures, To stay current on my subject, Aware of technical developments, I use online learning materials to help me, To make personal learning easier, To learn about topics outside of my major, and To view online videos of teaching. For the other factor 10 the estimated significance value is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing there is a significant difference among male and female between the purposes of accessing OER, viz., to gain access to free online learning resources.

The objective of using open educational resources (OER) is detailed in Table 6. On the Likert scale, we measure the following values: 1-never, 2-rarely, 3-occasionally, 4-often, and 5-very regularly are the five options. We'll start with option 1. Access relevant learning materials, which have a mode value of 3; the second is we look at to keep track of notes. It has a mode value of four. The third is to be aware of current facts and figures, which has a mode value of 3. The fourth is to stay current on my subject, which has a mode value of 4. The fifth, with a mode value of 4, is Aware of technical developments. The sixth is that I use online learning materials to help me. It has a mode value of 4. The ninth option is to view online videos of teaching, which has a mode value of 3. Finally, its mode value is 4 to gain access to free online learning resources. Students are adopting OER; however they are not completely utilizing open educational resources, as shown in this table (OER).

Table 7: Benefits of using OER

[1- Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neutral, 4- Agree, 5- Strongly Agree.]

S. No	Benefits of using OER	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D
1	Sharing of global learning resources among contemporary learners	7	12	34	41	18	3.46	4.00	4	1.081
		6.3 %	10.7 %	30.4 %	36.6 %	16.1 %				
2	Encourage students to develop their skills.	6	9	32	46	19	3.56	4.00	4	1.038
		5.4 %	8 %	28.6 %	41.1 %	17 %				
3	Chances to compare notes and lectures from around the world	5	7	38	37	25	3.63	4.00	3	1.041
		4.5 %	6.3 %	33.9 %	33 %	22.3 %				

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4	Access to audio/video recordings of various course lectures	4	12	31	45	20	3.58	4.00	4	1.019
		3.6 %	10.7 %	27.7 %	40.2 %	17.9 %				
5	Students who are financially disadvantaged can obtain learning resources at a low cost.	2	13	41	33	23	3.55	3.50	3	1.003
		1.8 %	11.6 %	36.6 %	29.5 %	20.5 %				
6	It helps you save time, money, and energy.	6	13	27	41	25	3.59	4.00	4	1.119
		5.4 %	11.6 %	24.1 %	36.6 %	22.3 %				
7	It aids in the preparation of projects and assignments.	3	5	36	35	33	3.80	4.00	3	1.003
		2.7 %	4.5 %	32.1 %	31.3 %	29.5 %				
8	Learning can take place anywhere and at any time.	6	11	35	40	20	3.51	4.00	4	1.065
		5.4 %	9.8 %	31.3 %	35.7 %	17.9 %				

The advantages of using OER are detailed in Table 7. The following are the options: On the Likert scale, the following values are measured: The following are the five possibilities: 1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, and 5-Strongly agree are the five possible responses. The first is Sharing of global learning resources among contemporary learners, which has a Mode value of 4, and the second is Encourage students to develop their skills, which has a Mode value of 4, Chances to compare notes and lectures from around the world, according to the third, which has a mean value of 3. Access to audio/video recordings of various course lectures, which has a mean value of 4, is the fourth point, The fifth viewpoint is that students who are financially disadvantaged can obtain learning resources at a low cost, which has a mode value of 3, and the sixth viewpoint is that it helps you save time, money, and energy, which has a mode value of 4, and the seventh viewpoint is that it assists in the preparation of projects and assignments, which has a mode value of 3, and the final viewpoint is that learning can take place, which has a mode value of 4. All of the criteria in this table show that students should be aware of OER and that they must benefit from it.

Conclusion and Suggestion

For this study, participants were contacted to determine the impact of open educational resources on students from rural backgrounds. 112 users made efforts in this study through OER. The majority of users have an ICD device of their own, with most of them utilizing mobile devices, followed by laptops and computers. And they encounter particular challenges when trying to access OER information. In particular, they concur that there is a need for more OER training and that some OER resources are difficult to understand because of language barriers. However, the majority of them agree that using OER is useful for keeping track of notes, staying up to date on their field, staying aware of technological advancements, using online resources for self-help, learning about subjects unrelated to their major, and gaining access to free learning resources. Most users concur that OER benefits include encouraging students to strengthen their skills, encouraging the sharing of global learning materials among modern learners, and Access to audio and video recordings of various course lectures allowing for learning to occur anywhere and at any time while saving time, money, and energy. Students have some knowledge of OER for this study, but not all of it and not for all. Because of these findings, it can be concluded that although students are willing to learn about and use OER, they lack the necessary training. As a result, we suggest the government, organizations should support OER and educational institutions are conducting more awareness-raising and orientation campaigns about OER. Additionally, provide teachers and students with the necessary training on how to use open educational resources. And include a lesson on open educational resources in the curriculum for students at the school level; it will benefit them as future college students. As a further study, it would be good to conduct a similar study aimed at creating awareness or introducing students to these open educational resources. The study can be conducted in terms of how to attract more people and what to do to

motivate them to use.

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Reference

- [1] Arimoto, M., Barroca, L., & Barbosa, E. F. (2016). Developing open educational resources through learning design and agile practices. https://oro.open.ac.uk/47513/2/paperInfEdu1603-003_finalVersionORO.pdf
- [2] Declaration, P. (2012). Paris OER Declaration, 2012 World Open Educational Resources (OER) Congress. https://iite.unesco.org/files/news/639202/Paris%20OER%20Declaration_01.pdf
- [3] Hu, E., Li, Y., Li, J., & Huang, W. H. (2015). Open educational resources (OER) usage and barriers: a study from Zhejiang University, China. *Educational Technology Research and Development*
- [4] Kalaiyarasan, G. (2019). A Study On Usage Of Open Educational Resources (Oer) Format To Enhancing The Academic Performance Of Higher Secondary School Students In Ramanathapuram Educational District, Library Philosophy and Practice. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=6959&context=libphilprac>
- [5] Kumar, K. S., Fathurochman, I., Prabu, M. M., Ramnath, R., & Kumar, N. S. (2021). Usage and performance of open educational resources among state universities of tamil nadu research scholars. *Regular Issue*, 5(10), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijmh.i1311.0651021>
- [6] Nagaiah, M., & Thanuskodi, S. (2021). Utilization of open educational resources (OERs) among college students affiliated to Alagappa university in India. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S3), 1384-1399. <https://lingcure.org/index.php/journal/article/view/1822>
- [7] Nagaiah, M., Thanuskodi, S., & Alagu, A. AWARENESS AND USE OF OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN COLLEGE STUDENTS IN THE SIVAGANGA DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357777539>

TEXT MINING BASED CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS USING KTPLSA AND SLRBI-LSTM FOR BUSINESS GROWTH

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Abstract

On account of the potential for business growth, social networks in business are achieving unparalleled fame. Concerning the company's operations and their products/services they provide, the thoughts communicated on Social Media (SM) allow them to ascertain individual perceived strengths and weaknesses. Thus, for customer mindset prediction for business growth, an efficient Text Mining (TM) methodology by utilizing new Kendall's Tau Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (KTPLSA) and SoftLog-Relu activation espoused Bi-directional Long Short Term Memory (SLRBI-LSTM) method, has been proposed. At first, pre-processing is performed by amassing the input twitter dataset. Next, for the proficient analysis of Customer Behaviors (CBs) for diverse business applications, topic modelling with KTPLSA, Keyword extraction, Word embedding via Gaussian radial basis function, kernel-centered Global Vectors for word representation (G- Glove), and lastly classification of CB utilizing SLRBI-LSTM are carried out. The proposed technique's results are done, which confirms that the proposed technique surpassed other top- notch methods.

Keywords: *Text Mining, Social Media Analytics, Topic Modelling, Sentiment Analysis*

Introduction

Recently, diverse business models and companies have been consolidated by the invention of new technologies that reformed their schemes for this new digital ecosystem by developing and expanding their competencies in information and knowledge extraction [1]. In redefining the nature of how companies strategize their business processes, SM plays a vital function [2]. Since SM explicates CB and feedback regarding specific business proposals, services, and products, it has a decisive effect on the domain of business, advertisement, and e-commerce [3]. It is a network service that permits people to develop and send messages to another person who utilizes a similar service [4]. For extracting insights and finding knowledge regarding digital environments, the data produced by users on these networks has been extensively wielded by researchers [5]. To share and convey information and updates regarding products and services, Twitter has turned out to be one of the common media for online retailers and customers amongst the different SM platforms [6]. An extremely efficient method is required with a huge quantity of information flowing from SM for summarizing and retrieving information in a real-time circumstance [7]. Online reviews express valuable and decisive meanings to their readers, namely business managers and customers because they encompass the voice of the customers [8]. For the research of Sentiment Analysis (SA), a current stream of study deploys Data Mining (DM), which could be stated as a natural expansion of information technology and a fellowship of a few subject domains and associated application fields [9]. Text data collections like documents, web pages, articles, abstracts, news, and tweets are handled by TM, which is considered the main subfield of DM [10]. The process of gathering meaning from a huge number of data is termed TM [11]. The transformational process is assigned by TM and can refurbish unstructured data into a structured form for DM [12]. The way to identify people's opinions, attitudes, and emotions from text data that is obtainable on diverse platforms on the internet is called SA [13]. The classification of people's opinions, users, or customers of any product or service regarding the product or service they are utilizing as positive, negative, or neutral is delineated as SA [14]. The significance of this method is derived from its capability to comprehend sentiment polarities from large amounts of texts, and it has formerly been deployed to examine review opinion [15]. Currently, there is wide usage of Machine Learning (ML) methods to extract online reviews [16]. For extracting and detecting sentiment from data, the ML method wielded algorithms. Deep learning is the key to the big data epoch because the usual ML methods and Neural Networks (NNs) were not sufficient to acquire this big data [17]. If the size of the text corpus is huge and manual content investigation is not feasible, TM becomes necessary [18]. For CB investigations utilizing a TM method, a new KTPLSA and SLRBI-LSTM technique is

proposed for the expansion of business. The leftover work is arranged as follows: Section (2) exhibits the literature review. The proposed technique is explicated in section (3). Section (4) elucidates the outcomes and discussion. Finally, the conclusion and the future scope are provided in section (5).

Literature Review

Nalini Chintalapudi et.al [19] designed TM on real-time medical records of seafarers to produce superior knowledge of medical problems that often occurred on board. Pre- processing, Document Term Matrix development, and SA were encompassed. With above 80% of accuracy and precision, the findings confirmed this method. Conversely, adequate accuracy was not acquired by this system. Shailendra Kumar Singh and & Manoj Kumar Sachan [20] put forward model of SentiVerb and Spell Checker system that extracted the reaction, mood, along with opinion of users from SM Text (SMT). Centered on the sentiment score of SMT, the positive or negative opinions were categorized utilizing a Dictionary-Based Approach (DBA) and a binary classifier. When weighed against the prevailing algorithms, this model wielded a Rule-Based Classifier (RBC), which exhibited a good performance outcome. Inaccurate sentiment scoring of opinion words by the prevailing lexicons was the disadvantage possessed by the DBA. Byeongki Jeong et.al [21] created an opportunity mining method to find product opportunities centered on topic modelling and SA of SM data. Latent product topics and satisfaction levels were recognized by this method utilizing SA. At last, by employing an opportunity algorithm, the opportunity value and improvement direction were found. When weighed against the baseline systems, the outcomes evinced enhanced performance. In contrast, the method's performance was degraded by the prerequisite of a fixed number of topics in the utilized topic modelling method. Qingyuan Zhou et.al [22] presented textual sentiment calculation and fuzzy mathematics for studying the online consumers' online repurchase goals. A system was developed grounded on emotional computing along with fuzzy reasoning by considering satisfaction, trust, and promotion efforts as the antecedents together with consumer repurchase intention as the consequent. The suggested techniques' results surpassed the current methodologies. However, the evaluation to predict the online reviews' degree might not be concentrated deeply and specifically. Farkhund Iqbal et.al [23] intended a hybrid SA system by merging ML and lexicon-centric approaches. Pre-processing, Parts of Speech (PSO) tagging, feature extraction, feature optimization, along with SA are the encompassed steps. When weighed against the prevailing methodology, this system exhibited enhanced accuracy. Nevertheless, the accuracy was less since the Genetic Algorithm (GA) has the over-fitting issue for feature reduction.

Proposed Framework

By utilizing a TM, a fresh KTPLSA and SLRBi-LSTM methodology is proposed for customer behaviour evaluation to develop business. Grounded on SM review, various steps are wielded for effectively evaluating the customer's mindsets. For analysis, Twitter data is espoused. In figure 1, the TM architecture is expounded.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed work

Preprocessing

By employing Application Program Interface (API), the customer tweets are gathered. For structuring

the unstructured input, pre-processing is conducted. The procedure of cleaning and transforming the input for effectual outcomes is termed pre-processing. The pre-process steps are,

Data splitting: Here, for evaluation, the bunch of tweets generated is partitioned into several distinct words. Evaluating the topic or opinion to be analogized if there are any modifications in tweets sentiment along with topics grounded on business is the aim.

Case transformation: It is used to standardize the data. The conversion of letters, words, and sentences that are in upper case are encompassed in case transformation. For maintaining the text's uniformity, toggle cases are converted into lower case.

Data cleaning: Since it eliminates unnecessary details such as (i) URLs, (ii) numbers, (iii) punctuation marks, (iv) alphanumeric characters, et cetera, to make the data readable for processing it plays a major role in pre-processing.

Infrequent terms removal: To recognize the structure and type of tweets, it removes the unused words from the input and identifies the frequently used words. **POS tagging:** Since they are significant parameters of opinion, this categorizes the nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc.

$$P_i = (P_{i1}, P_{i2}, \dots, P_{in}) \quad (1)$$

Topic Modelling with KTPLSA

For CB analysis, it categorizes a group of words (topic) from the corpus of pre-processed tweets that best represents the information. To understand the hidden semantic structures, it is one among the most widely used TM techniques. PLSA calculates the probability of word occurrences in a text and maps them under several topics. If any two words have a high proportion of similarity in a specific topic, it looks like both are more likely to that topic than others, which is a major drawback. Thus, mis-modelling of words is caused by a topic. Thus, for determining the appropriate relation between every word, KT computation is done. Therefore, PLSA becomes KTPLSA.

probability of words in topic is signified by $pr\left(\frac{P_i}{\phi}\right)$, probability of random words $(\cdot, \cdot)$ in (ϕ) becomes $pr\left(\frac{\cdot}{\phi}\right)$. Next, the probability of words in the tweets is calculated as,

$$pr\left(\frac{P_i}{\cdot}\right) = \sum_{\phi=1}^K pr(\phi)^{\theta_i} \left(pr\left(\frac{P_i}{\phi}\right) \cdot pr\left(\frac{\cdot}{\phi}\right) \right) \quad \dots$$

By employing expectation maximization, the probability of each word is analyzed. Expectation estimates the probability of words on the topic,

$$pr(\phi_k | P_i, \cdot) = \frac{pr(\phi_k)^{\theta_i} \cdot pr\left(\frac{P_i}{\phi_k}\right) \cdot pr\left(\frac{\cdot}{\phi_k}\right)}{\sum_{\phi=1}^K pr(\phi)^{\theta_i} \cdot pr\left(\frac{P_i}{\phi}\right) \cdot pr\left(\frac{\cdot}{\phi}\right)} \quad (3)$$

Here, the probability of words related to that specific topic is depicted by θ_i . For calculating the update values of tweets in a topic, the maximization is done. The probability of (P_i) , $(\cdot, \cdot)$ in (ϕ) and tweets (τ) becomes the KTPLSA outcome.

$$pr(\cdot, \cdot | P_i) = \frac{\sum_{\phi=1}^K pr(\tau_i | \cdot, \cdot) \cdot pr(\phi | \tau_i, \cdot, \cdot)}{\sum_{\phi=1}^K \sum_{i=1}^M M(\tau_i | \cdot, \cdot) \cdot pr(\phi_k | \tau_{i\phi}, P_i)} \quad (4)$$

$$pr(\phi_k | P_i) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M M(P_i | \tau_i) \cdot pr(\phi_k | \tau_{i\phi}, P_i)}{M_{\tau_i}} \quad (5)$$

By utilizing the below equation, the similarity between each word in a specific topic $\square\square\square$ is compared.

Thus, for further analysis, the words related to specific topics are modelled and then keywords are

$$KT(\dots) = \frac{(\dots)}{n * m(n-1)(m-1)} \tag{6}$$

extracted from these topics of words.

Keyword Extraction

The words that are significant to evaluate CBs for the classification are termed keywords. Various aspects like adjectives, verbs, and nouns are extracted. For detecting the tweets’ polarity that is helpful to find the individuals’ opinions, their aspects are detected as positive or negative. The key features, which are wielded for the classification task, are handled as feature vectors.

$$x_f = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_F\} \tag{7}$$

Here, the number of extracted keywords is elucidated by F .

G-Glove Embedding

By encoding the meaning of the words, which bridges the gap between human understandings of language to that of the machine, word embedding defines the real-valued vector representation of words; in addition, enhances the classification accuracy. In a textual corpus, it is grounded on word occurrences along with keeps track of the frequency of co- occurrences of word pairs. Nevertheless, the high frequency of occurrences affects the embedding process during the frequency of word co-occurrence calculation; thus, mis- classification is caused. To adjust the high frequent co-occurrences, the system uses a Gaussian RBF kernel. Thus, it is termed G-Glove.

Step 1: Consider, X be the word-to-word co-occurrence matrix, and $x_{f,q}$ detects the frequency of word that f takes place in the context q , formulated as,

$$X_f = \sum_r x_{f,q} \tag{8}$$

Step 2: Next, the probability of a word f appears in q $\Pr(f,q)$ could be expressed as,

$$\Pr(f,q) = \Pr\left(\frac{f}{q}\right) = \frac{X_{f,q}}{q} \tag{9}$$

Step 3: The objective function (Ψ) can be defined based on the ratio of word co-occurrence probability.

$$\Psi = \sum_{f,q} \zeta(X_{f,q}) (X_{f,q}^T X_{f,q} + W_{bf} + W_{bq} - \exp^{-1}(1 + X_{f,q})^2) \tag{10}$$

Where, the bias values of words are signified by W_{bf}, W_{bq} , and the weighting function to adjust the high frequent co-occurrences of words is depicted by $\zeta(X_{f,q})$.

Step 4: For regulating the high frequent co-occurrences of words, the Gaussian RBF kernel is equated as,

$$\zeta(X_{f,q}) = \exp\left[-\frac{\|X_{f,q} - X_{f,q}\|^2}{2\sigma^2} * \Pr(f,q)\right] \tag{11}$$

The word similarity, the number of word-word co-occurrence count, and probability of occurrences are detected by the Glove methodology along with maps the word into its corresponding real vector. The attained vector representation of words,

$$\mathbf{z}^{(t)} = \mathbf{z}^{(t)}, \mathbf{z}^{(t)}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{(t)} \tag{12}$$

Behavior Analysis via SLRBi-LSTM

To categorize the vectors into positive, negative, and neutral sentiments, which aid in the development of business, the SLRBi-LSTM classification is presented. For data storage, cell state preservation, and to regulate the cell states, Bi-LSTM, which is a classification system, includes input, forget, along with output gates. The disadvantage is: since the influence of a provided input on the hidden layer either decays or blows up exponentially over time (vanishing gradient issue), the gamut of context that could be accessed is partial. With the SLR activation, which surpasses the vanishing gradient issue along with enhances the computational speed, an effectual viewpoint, along with the sigmoid activation function to get the output of the input, forget, and output gate are modified. It is also termed SLRBi- LSTM. In figure 2, the Bi-LSTM’s architecture is expounded.

Figure 2: Structure of Bi-LSTM

In the network with SLR (S_{lr}) and tanh (T_{an}) activation function, the input gate ($i(t)$), forget gate ($f(t)$), cell state ($\kappa(t)$), along with output gate ($z(t)$) at time t for the input $\mathbf{g}^{(i)}$ with the hidden states $h(t)$ and $h(t-1)$ along with the weight and bias functions ($w_i, b_i, w_f, b_f, w_\kappa, b_\kappa, w_z, b_z$) of every gates is equated as,

$$i(t) = \sigma(\mathbf{h}(t) \cdot [w_i(t-1), \mathbf{g}^{(i)}] + b_i) \tag{13}$$

$$z(t) = S_{lr}(\mathbf{b}_z + [h(t-1), f(t)] * w_z) \tag{15}$$

$$\kappa(t) = (1 - \chi) * \{f(t) * h(t-1) + i(t) * T_{an}(\mathbf{b}_\kappa + [h(t-1), \mathbf{g}^{(i)}] * w_\kappa)\} \tag{16}$$

$$z(t) = S_{lr}(\mathbf{b}_z + [h(t-1), \mathbf{g}^{(i)}] * w_z) \tag{17}$$

Here, the tuneable parameter used to neglect the gradient component suppression is signified by $\chi \in (0,1)$. The hidden state output is given by,

$$h(t) = z(t) * T_{an}(\kappa(t)) \tag{18}$$

The tanh activation function (T_{an}) is formulated as,

$$T_{an}(\mathbf{g}^{(i)}) = \frac{e^{-\mathbf{g}^{(i)}} - e^{\mathbf{g}^{(i)}}}{e^{\mathbf{g}^{(i)} + 1} + e^{-\mathbf{g}^{(i)} + 1}} \tag{19}$$

The SLR (S_{lr}) is expressed as,

$$S_{lr}(\mathbf{g}^{(i)}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{g}^{(i)} & \mathbf{g}^{(i)} \leq 0 \\ \frac{\mathbf{g}^{(i)}}{1 + |\mathbf{g}^{(i)}|} & \alpha \geq \mathbf{g}^{(i)} > 0 \\ \log(\gamma - \mathbf{g}^{(i)} + 1) + |\log(\gamma - \alpha + 1) - \alpha| & \mathbf{g}^{(i)} > \alpha \end{cases} \tag{20}$$

Here, the random integers between 0 and 1 are depicted by $\square, \square$. Centered on the extracted tweets, the system engenders the output as positive, negative, and neutral sentences, which will be helpful for the development and growth of business in the future. In figure 3, the pseudo-code of the proposed work is given.

Pseudocode of the proposed text mining approach

Input: Twitter data ($y_k = y_1, y_2, \dots, y_M$)

Output: Classified sentiments (π_m)

Begin

Initialize business associated twitter data (y_k)

While ($k < M$)

For each k

Carry out preprocessing

Attain $\rho_i = (\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_n)$

For every $1 \leq i \leq n$

Execute topic modelling

Evaluate the probability of $(\rho_i), (\lambda_j)$ in (ϕ)

Measure $KT(\lambda_j, \rho_i | \phi_k)$

End for

Extract $x_f = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p\}$

For each f

Implement $X_f = \sum_i x_{f_i}, \mathfrak{R}(f, q)$

Estimate the objective function (Ψ)

Calculate $\xi(X_{f_i})$

End for

Recognize $\mathcal{G}^{(j)} \rightarrow$ vector representation of words

For $1 \leq j \leq F$

Input $\mathcal{G}^{(j)}$ to SLRBi-LSTM

Calculate $(i(t)), (f(t)), (\kappa(t))$, and $z(t)$

Evaluate $h(t) = z(t) * T_{in}(\kappa(t))$

For each t

Compute T_{in}, S_{in} activation function

End for

End for

End for

End while

Accomplish (π_m)

End

Figure 3: Pseudocode of the proposed system

Results and Discussion

For analyzing the performance, the proposed system's results are weighed against state-of-art techniques. The openly accessible Twitter dataset is wielded along with is implemented in the working platform of PYTHON.

The output comparison is as follows.

Performance of proposed SLRBI-LSTM

Here, the proposed SLRBI-LSTM's efficacy is analogized to the prevailing Bi-LSTM, Long term Short Term Memory (LSTM), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Recurrent NN (RNN). Regarding accuracy, precision, F-Measure (FM), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), along with Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), the measurements are conducted. In table1, the performance assessment is publicized.

Table 1: Performance assessment of SLRBI-LSTM with existing classifiers

TECHNIQUES	ACCURACY(%)	PRECISION(%)	F-MEASURE(%)
Proposed SLRBI-LSTM	98.4586	98.2571	98.2047
Bi-LSTM	96.1247	97.0458	96.4105
LSTM	95.0412	95.1435	94.9954
MLP	93.9874	94.6471	93.1386
RNN	92.3542	93.2348	92.8945

Regarding accuracy, precision, and FM, the proposed SLRBI-LSTM's superiority is exhibited in table 1. For accuracy, precision, and FM, the SLRBI-LSTM attains the highest value of 98.4586%, 98.2571%, and 98.2047%; while, the prevailing system attained the lower value of 96.1247%, 97.0458%, and 96.4105% respectively; in addition, the remaining prevailing systems like LSTM, MLP, and RNN also attained lower values comparatively. Thus, regarding the accuracy, precision, and FM, the SLRBI-LSTM attains superior performance.

Figure 4: Performance comparison in terms of MAE and RMSE

The proposed SLRBI-LSTM's error estimation with other prevailing methodologies is signified in figure 4. The sample size by the absolute errors is termed MAE. The standard deviation of prediction errors is termed RMSE. Regarding MAE and RMSE, the SLRBI-LSTM attained lower error value of 4.2356% and 10.2346%; whereas, the prevailing techniques attained a higher error value of (6.3155%; 15.3264%) for Bi-LSTM, (10.2464%; 17.2356%) for LSTM, (13.2468%; 20.6413%) for MCP, and (15.2346%; 22.5136%) for RNN. Thus, when analogized to the prevailing system, the SLRBI-LSTM has a minimal error.

Figure 5: performance of proposed SLRBI-LSTM in terms of training time

The proposed SLRBI-LSTM’s training time is analogized to the current techniques in figure 5. For training the data, the SLRBI-LSTM takes less time of 55.2314 sec; while, the prevailing methodologies take huge time. Thus, the SLRBI-LSTM utilizes less time to train the data.

Performance Analysis Of Proposed Kplsta

Regarding accuracy, recall, sensitivity, and specificity, the proposed KPTLSA is weighed against the prevailing Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (PLSA), Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), together with Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA).

Table 2: accuracy, recall, sensitivity, and specificity assessment

Techniques	Accuracy	Recall	Sensitivity	Specificity
Proposed KPTLSA	98.4561	98.2346	98.7464	98.8974
PLSA	95.2155	96.1564	96.4464	96.7953
LSA	94.4616	95.1154	94.3342	95.0212
LDA	92.0154	93.1242	93.0452	93.1241

Regarding accuracy, recall, sensitivity, and specificity, the increasing character of the proposed KPTLSA with existing techniques are elucidated in Table 2. Grounded on the accuracy, recall, sensitivity, and specificity, the KPTLSA acquired a higher value of 98.4561%, 98.2346%, 98.7464%, and 98.8974%; while the prevailing PLSA attained a value of 95.2155%, 96.1564%, 96.4464%, and 96.7953%, which is relatively low; addition, the remaining prevailing methodologies also depicted lower values for every metric. Thus, when weighed against the current systems, the KPTLSA exhibited enhanced performance.

Performance Of Proposed G-Glove

Grounded on accuracy and FM, the proposed G-Glove is analogized to the prevailing Glove, word 2 vec, and Bidirectional Encoders Representations from Transformers (BERT).

Figure 6: Performance of proposed G-Glove in terms of accuracy and f-measure

The proposed G-Glove is analogized to the prevailing methodologies in figure 6. For recall and FM, the G-Glove attains a higher value of 98.2315 % and 98.7955%; whereas, the prevailing glove, word 2 vec, and BERT achieved the value of (96.4616%,97.4216%), (94.1646%,95.7464%) and (92.4134%,94.1464%). Thus when weighed against the prevailing system, the G-Glove exhibits higher performance by attaining higher values regarding metrics.

Conclusion

For business growth, an efficient TM methodology utilizing a new KTPLSA and SLRBI- LSTM technique is proposed for customer mindset prediction. Pre-processing, topic modelling, keyword extraction, word embedding, and classification are the steps entailed in the proposed method. For accuracy, FM, precision, and sensitivity, the proposed method achieved a peak value in the classification of 98.2315%, 98.7955%, 98.2751%, and 98.7464%. When analogized to the prevailing models, namely BERT, RNN, LSTM, and BI- LSTM, the training time (55.2314sec) required for the proposed model is low. Thus, it is clear that the proposed system is superior to other prevailing techniques. By utilizing an advanced neuro mining method, this work can be enhanced in the future, which will facilitate organizations to acquire a deeper understanding of consumers.

References

- [1] Jose Ramon Saura and Dag R Bennett, "A three-stage method for data text mining using UGC in business intelligence analysis", *Symmetry*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1-13, 2019.
- [2] Alrence Santiago Halibas, Abubucker Samsudeen Shaffi and Mohamed Abdul Kader Varusai Mohamed, "Application of text classification and clustering of twitter data for business analytics", *Majan International Conference (MIC)*, 19-20 March 2018, Muscat, Oman, 2018.
- [3] Shaha Al-Otaibi, Allulo Alnassar, Asma Alshahrani, Amany Al-Mubarak, Sara Albugami, Nada Almutiri and Aisha Albugami, "Customer satisfaction measurement using sentiment analysis", *(IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 106-117, 2018.
- [5] Mehdi Emadi and Mehdi Emadi, "Twitter sentiment analysis using fuzzy integral classifier fusion", *Journal of Information Science*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551519828627>.
- [6] Jose Ramon Saura, Ana Reyes-Menendez and Pedro Palos-Sanchez, "Are black friday deals worth it? mining twitter users' sentiment and behavior response", *Journal of Open Innovation Technology Market and Complexity*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 1-13, 2019.
- [7] Noor Farizah Ibrahim and Xiaojun Wang, "A text analytics approach for online retailing service improvement evidence from Twitter", *Decision Support Systems*, vol. 121, pp. 37-50, 2019.
- [8] Andry Alamsyah, Wirawan Rizkika, Ditya Dwi Adhi Nugroho, Farhan Renaldi and Siti Saadah, "Dynamic large scale data on twitter using sentiment analysis and topic modeling", *6th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT)*, 03-05 May 2018, Bandung, Indonesia, 2018.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

STUDY ON OUTCOME-BASED EDUCATION AND EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

The Indian system of education sustained Indian civilization for centuries. The European system of higher education was introduced in India by the British Rulers with the main aim of colonizing the country culturally and producing a work force to serve the British administration. The then education system never encouraged a spirit of critical enquiry or independent thinking which is essential for advancement of knowledge.

Introduction

Higher education of a country powers the supply of skilled and technologically advanced manpower which would in turn lead to growth and development of a country. The higher education system followed in India still continues to have a colonial hangover. Post-independence India adopted the socialistic pattern of planning which laid emphasis on industrialization. In line with the same the Government invested heavily in setting up of technical educational institutions. In India Higher Education begins after 12 (10+2) years of primary, secondary and senior secondary education. Higher Education is provided by various types of institutions like universities, colleges, institutes of national importance, polytechnics etc. Universities are also of different types such as State University, Deemed University, Central University, Private University etc. India has a federal set-up and the Indian constitution places education as a concurrent responsibility of both the center and state, where the center co-ordinates and fixes standards in higher and technical education.

Benefits of Outcome-based Education

Clarity: The focus on outcomes creates a clear expectation of what needs to be accomplished by the end of the course. Students will understand what is expected of them and teachers will know what they need to teach during the course. Clarity is important over years of schooling and when team teaching is elaborate. Each team member and year in school will have a clear understanding of what needs to be talented in each class, or at each level, allowing students to develop.

Flexibility: With a clear sense of what needs to be skilled, instructors will be able to construct their lessons around the student's needs. Outcome-based education does not specify a specific method of instruction, leaving instructors free to teach their students using any technique. Instructors will also be able to recognize diversity among students by using several teaching and assessment techniques during their classes. Outcome-based education is intended to be a model. Student-centered learning.

Comparison: Outcome-based education can be compared across different institutions. On an individual level, institutions can look at what outcomes a student has achieved to decide what level the student would be at within a new institution. On an institutional level, institutions can compare themselves, by checking to see what outcomes they have in common, and find places where they may need development, based on the achievement of outcomes at other institutions. The ability to compare easily across institutions allows students to move between institutions with relative ease. The institutions can compare outcomes to determine what credits to award the student. The clearly expressed outcomes should allow institutions to assess the student's achievements rapidly, leading to increased movement of students.

Involvement: Student involvement in the classroom is a key part of outcome-based education. Students are expected to do their own learning so that they gain a full thoughtful of the material. Increased student involvement allows students to feel responsible for their own learning, and they should learn more through this individual learning. Other characteristics of involvement are parental and community, through developing curriculum, or making changes to it. Outcome-based education outcomes are meant to be decided upon within a school system.

Employability skills: Employability skills include the soft skills that allow you to work well with others,

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

apply knowledge to solve problems and fit into any work situation. They also include the professional skills that enable you to be successful in the workplace. These are also considered transferable skills because you can apply them to a job in any industry. Employability skills are the core skills and traits needed in nearly every job (Alison Doyle, 2020). These are the general skills that make someone desirable to an organization. Hiring managers almost always look for employees with these skills.

Types of Employability Skills

Communication

All employers look for job candidates with strong communication skills. These refer to one's ability to convey information clearly to others. Employers want employees with strong written, verbal, and nonverbal communication skills (Alison Doyle, 2020). Part of being a strong communicator also includes being a good listener; employees need to be able to understand the questions and concerns of their clients and listen to their employer's directions.

- 1) Written Communication
- 2) Oral Communication Interpersonal Skills
- 3) Active Listening
- 4) Attentive

Teamwork

Teamwork is important in almost any work setting. If an employee works on a number of group projects, they need to be able to get along well with others and carry their share of the workload. Even if an employee does not do a lot of team projects, they still need to be able to work well with colleagues and managers (Alison Doyle, 2020).

Critical Thinking

According to Alison Doyle (2020) stated that critical thinking refers to your ability to understand, analyze, and interpret information and draw conclusions. In any job, an employee will have to assess situations and solve problems. Employees need to think logically and make sensible judgments.

Ethics

Employees who understand and follow company rules, are honest and trustworthy, and act professionally and responsibly (Alison Doyle, 2020).

- 1) Compliance
- 2) Integrity
- 3) Empathy
- 4) Discernment

Conclusion

The outcome-based education is dependent on the employability skills of university graduate students. Outcome-based education and is significant predictor the employability skills of university graduate students with the magnitude of 73% of variance.

References

- [1] Doyle, A. (2020). Scaling the mountain: The topography of disability and transition to higher education in Ireland (Doctoral dissertation, Trinity College Dublin).
- [2] Bhaffor, K. A., Radzak, M. Y., & Abdullah, C. H. (2017). Students' perception on outcome-based education (OBE) implementation: a preliminary study in UniKL MSI.
- [3] University Kuala Lumpur Malaysian Spanish Institute, Kulim Hi-Tech Park, 9000.
- [4] Tan, H. E., Oriah, A., & Senian, M. (2012). Implementation of Outcome-based Education Incorporating Technology Innovation. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 62, 649-655.
- [5] Ward, V. G., & Riddle, D. I. (2003). Measuring employment readiness. *NATCON Papers* 2003.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

MULTICULTURALISM IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

An idea, a movement for educational reform, and a method are all parts of multicultural education (Banks, 1997). Multicultural education is a concept that aims to give all students, regardless of their racial, ethnic, or social background, access to equal educational opportunities. By altering the entire school environment to reflect the various cultures and groups that exist in a society and in the country's classrooms, multicultural education aims to provide equitable educational opportunities for all pupils. Because its objectives are ideals that educators and administrators should work tirelessly to realise, multicultural education is a process. Helping students gain the information and commitments necessary to make thoughtful decisions and to engage in personal, social, and civic action to advance democracy and democratic living is a key objective of multicultural education.

Introduction

Cultural variety is multiculturalism. The goal of multiculturalism is to appreciate other cultures and accord them an equal status under the law. No one culture in the nation should supplant others to the point of extinction. Any culture's future is dependent on the ideology of the educated class in that nation, hence that nation's educational system has an impact on that culture. Since education is a tool for growing, preserving, and transforming culture, it is crucial to instil multiculturalism in education in a nation like India that has embraced multiculturalism and secularism. India is a country with many diverse faiths, dialects, educational systems, traditions, and values. Indian culture was created by followers of several religions.

Meaning of Multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is the practise of treating all religions and individuals from all cultures equally and without making any differences based on race or ethnicity.

Needs and Importance of Multiculturalism in Education

To identifications of the culture: In addition to introducing pupils to various cultures, multicultural education fosters in them a respect for other cultures in addition to their own, as well as sensitivity and empathy for those cultures. To create cultural Integration: Through multicultural education, it is possible to promote cultural integration among students. The integrity of the entire nation benefits from cultural fusion as well. The Benefits and Consequences of Cultural Integration in Society aids in obtaining education in this area, multicultural education improves cultural integration, and it aids in cultivating a sense of community among many cultures in society. To develop responsible citizenship: The wealth of the nation is its knowledgeable and accountable populace. Any nation's development is based on the evolution of its society. Through intercultural education, responsible citizenship is quickly developed in such circumstances. Because of this, multicultural education is essential for producing capable citizens. To create broad positive social approaches: It is imperative to promote multicultural education in order to foster a broad, optimistic social vision. The formation of responsible citizenship through education depends largely on multicultural education. Because social growth cannot occur without fostering social awareness, multicultural education can help students develop a broad sense of social responsibility. It does, in fact, take time. For Cultural exchange: Each nation has its own unique culture, which is a great advantage. In a nation where culture is a way of life, it is actually thought that education plays a significant role in conserving and fostering culture. The ideas and values of cultural variety may be preserved and nurtured through multicultural education, and this is crucial for the growth of the country. In such a situation, cultural interchange encourages cultural integration and enhances the nation's cultural heritage.

Curriculum for Multicultural Education

Must be adaptable Flexibility in the curriculum is crucial for intercultural education. In order to achieve the purpose of education by balancing social variety and social traits, which should reflect various cultural elements, a flexible curriculum is of utmost importance. Should reflect the cultural needs and problems: For

intercultural inclusion, the multicultural education curriculum should be appropriately constructed. Through the multicultural education curriculum, students should be made aware of social demands and challenges. Because it is impossible to conceive about growth or the progress of any nation without awareness of socio-cultural demands and challenges, a multicultural curriculum is a crucial part of education. Should develop sensitivity: The multicultural education curriculum should help pupils develop their personalities, fostering in them an awareness of other cultures as well as a willingness to serve them and a sense of responsibility. This will support the growth of a community-welcoming mindset toward the kids and in general.

Multicultural Curriculum Teaching Methods

Project method: The correct implementation of the multicultural curriculum benefits greatly from the project method. By using the project technique, it is feasible to encourage multiculturalism in students. There are many different project kinds that can be conducted, such as gathering data on various social concerns, data on various cultural traits, and data on various environmental difficulties. Students can complete countless projects of this nature in this manner. **Problem solving method:** The teacher should assign the students' problem projects using problem-solving techniques in a society where there are numerous terrible customs and traditions in order for the students to find the appropriate resolution in the context of all of these wrong customs and traditions. For instance, the Honda technique identifies the root reasons of water scarcity and proposes a strategy for resolving the issue. The problem solving approach can be effectively applied in this way. **Seminar method:** Through the seminar teaching approach, it is possible to have a thorough debate on many socio-cultural themes. This is how the educational approach effectively instils in the students a sense of cultural proficiency, cultural brotherhood, and cultural awareness.

Obstacles of Multicultural Education

Lack of multicultural teaching strategies: If a multicultural mindset is to be ingrained in the children, the teacher must adopt a multicultural teaching strategy, yet most teachers do not adhere to the multicultural teaching work policy. When teachers use holistic teaching techniques, students become more interested in learning, but most teachers don't seem to be doing this, which makes it harder for pupils to adopt a multicultural perspective. **Lack of cultural awareness:** Building reciprocal cultural tolerance among pupils is extremely challenging when there is a lack of cultural awareness. Culture cannot be preserved, nurtured, or changed without cultural understanding. The absence of intercultural consciousness has made it challenging to create multicultural philosophy in society and among students. **Cultural conflicts:** A pre-existing conflict is cultural conflict. Prejudices towards one another's cultures are fostered via cultural conflict. It also aims to subjugate the majority culture in favour of the minority culture. Cultural conflict has therefore become a significant barrier for multicultural curriculum and cultural education. **Social inequality:** There are many various faiths, castes, ethnic groups, creeds, dialects, and genders in Indian culture. As a result, fostering a sense of oneness within society is challenging. Brotherly regard does not grow in the society in such a circumstance. Many marginalised groups are aware of the political and sociocultural injustice they are experiencing. Social disparity is a significant barrier to intercultural education, therefore.

Conclusion

The necessity for multicultural education is urgent. Multicultural education is crucial for fostering cultural respect, goodwill, preservation, nurturing, and transition in a secular country like India. The future of the educational system, as well as the growth of the nation, depend on a multicultural curriculum, multicultural learning instructional methods, equality in the classroom, a democratic school atmosphere, equality of opportunity, and the promotion of intercultural tolerance.

References

- [1] Banks, J. A. (1995a). Multicultural Education: Historical Development, Dimensions, and Practice. In J. A. Banks & C. A. M. Banks (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on Multicultural Education* (pp.3-24). New York: Macmillan.
- [2] Banks, J. A. (1995b). Multicultural Education: Its Effects on Students' Racial and Gender Role Attitudes. In J. A. Banks & C. A. M. Banks (Eds.). *Handbook of Research on Multicultural Education*

NEP 2020: PROMOTION OF TECHNOLOGY IN HOLISTIC EDUCATION WITH SYMBIOSIS OF METACOGNITION

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Abstract

The National Education Policy 2020 is the first such plan to be introduced in the 21st century. NEP 2020 provides a road map for progressing from early reading and numeracy to more advanced skills and understanding. Throughout NEP 2020, we recognise the value of science and technology. These days, India is a global competitor in information technology (IT) services, vaccine and pharmaceutical production, space missions, etc. There are, however, areas of science and technology where we currently lag the rest of the world. These include cyber safety, the manufacture of electrical components like CPUs, the manufacture of APIs, etc. NEP 2020 lays forth a plan to increase research in all areas of science and technology to help us learn more about them. The modern youth face some novel challenges and require some novel solutions. As a result, they now rely heavily on technology. The negative aspects of science and technology, such as cybercrime, will give rise to environmental concerns for them to solve. The major effect of NEP 2020 will be to provide Indians with the metacognitive tools they need to effectively combat current and future issues and to transform India into a scientifically and culturally sophisticated and richer, peaceful nation. A holistic education fosters a love of learning that will last a lifetime. The emphasis in the classroom shifts to helping students develop the attitudes, perspectives, and self-awareness they will need to thrive in today's interconnected and complex society. A student's emotional and intellectual growth, as well as their capacity to take on new experiences, gain new knowledge, and grow from their mistakes, are all bolstered by an education that takes a more comprehensive approach.

Keywords: *NEP 2020, Holistic Education, Technology, and Metacognition*

TECHNICAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Technical education is distinct from professional education, which places major emphasis upon the theories, understanding, and principles of a wide body of subject matter designed to equip the graduate to practice authoritatively in such fields as science, engineering, law, or medicine. Technical education covers engineering, architecture, management, planning, applied sciences, and other related fields. It helps to prepare students for a career where they can apply scientific and technical principles to create solutions. Professional education includes any programs that improve the knowledge, skills, attitudes, or behaviors of health care providers on the importance of breast-feeding, the physiology and management of lactation, or counselling related to breastfeeding. The aim of education is not only to literate a person, education should be self supporting. In the view of Mahatma Gandhi, 'Literacy in itself is no education'. Only becoming able to read and write books does not fulfil the aim of education. Education should help a person to become self dependent. For this, the importance of technical and professional education has taken place. The country which is strong in technical education becomes economically sound and developed. Technical and professional education helps a person to become self dependent or getting employed in any related sector instead of depending on government to provide him employment.

Keywords: *Technical Education, Professional Education.*

Introduction

The role of education in facilitating social and economic progress has long been recognized. Education improves functional and analytical ability and thereby opens up opportunities for individuals and also groups to achieve greater access to labour markets and livelihoods. A better educated labour force is essential if we are to meet the labour supply requirements of faster growth. Education is not only an instrument of enhancing efficiency but is also an effective tool of widening and augmenting democratic participation and upgrading the overall quality of individual and societal life. Skills and knowledge are the engines of economic growth and social development of any country. Countries with higher and better levels of knowledge and skills respond more effectively and promptly to challenges and opportunities of globalisation. India is in transition to a knowledge based economy and its competitive edge will be determined by the abilities of its people to create, share and use knowledge more effectively. This transition will require India to develop workers into knowledge workers who will be more flexible, analytical, adaptable and multi skilled. In the new knowledge economy the skill sets will include professional, managerial, operational, behavioural, inter personal and inter functional skills.

Necessity of Technical Education in India

In India, many people get education with higher degrees but stay unemployed after completing the education. Because they run after the government or private jobs and wait until they get a suitable job. Sometimes they don't get employment or get a job which doesn't match their qualification. This leads to frustration and harassment in the youth of our country. So, now a days the importance is given to technical or professional education. When a person is trained technically in a particular field, he does not depend on the jobs, he can become self employed by starting his own work. There are different fields of technical education like Agriculture, Veterinary, Engineering, Medical field etc. There are also short courses like tailoring, weaving, plumbing, typewriting, and in many other fields which helps people to be self employed. A person gets training and knowledge in a particular field which he can use as a path of earning to live his life and to support his family. Now a days, many institutes are providing technical and professional courses in our country. State wise technical education board has been set up to look after the necessity and importance of technical education and to implement it properly.

Technical Education Quality Improvement Programme

Government of India has implemented a Technical Quality Improvement Programme (TEQIP) with the assistance from the World Bank to improve the quality of education and enhance the capabilities of the technical institutions to become dynamic, demand-driven, quality conscious and competitive at national and international levels. The proposed reforms include faculty development, examination reforms, regular curriculum revision, introduction of semester system, focus on research and giving autonomy with the accountability.

University Grants Commission

The University Grants Commission has scheme of Career Orientation to Education / Career Oriented Programme / Career Oriented Courses. The objective of the scheme is to ensure that the graduates who pass out after completing these courses, have knowledge, skills and aptitude for gainful employment in wage sector, in general and self employment, in particular so as to reduce the pressure on institutions of higher learning for Master Degree. The courses run parallel to the conventional B.A., B.Com. and B.Sc. Degree. The successful students are awarded certificate/diploma/advanced diploma under this programme.

Structure of Indian Education System

The Indian education system works for primary education to research specialised education. It can be categorised as follows:

- 1) School Education & Literacy
 1. Primary Schooling
 2. Secondary Education
 3. Senior Secondary Education
- 2) Higher Education (Tertiary Education)
 1. Academic Degrees (Non-professional)
 2. Professional Degrees
 3. Technical Degrees
- 3) Vocational Education (Skilled Based)

Professional Education

A professional degree helps students prepare for careers in specific fields, such as law, pharmacy, medicine and education. Professional education is a formalized approach to specialized training in a professional school through which participants acquire content knowledge and learn to apply techniques. Incorporating the knowledge and values basic to a professional discipline. Understanding the central concepts, principles, and techniques applied in practice. Attaining a level of competence necessary for responsible entry into professional practice and Accepting responsibility for the continued development of competence.

Conclusion

Education system in India consists of Pre-primary, Primary /Elementary, Secondary and Higher Education Generally, there are three types of education at higher education level-General, Technical and Professional. General education is understood as education that focuses on the development of the students as individuals and puts them in touch with broad, yet focused courses that promote critical thinking and increase their awareness of the world around them. Core subjects taught at school like English, Maths, Science and Social Sciences form the bulk of general education courses, which are also taught at higher education level. With the onset of the 21st century, the entire world has witnessed an era of intense transformation in all areas, whether it is education, global trade and economy, technology or society. Recently, the covid-19 pandemic has also thrown up challenges for an individual and the nation, as a whole. Keeping into account these changes, a different skill-set is required by an individual to cope-up and succeed in facing the challenges in real-life, leading to her/his holistic progress. These skills are addressed as 21st Century Skills/ Learning Skills/ Transversal Competencies etc.

References

- [1] AISHE (2015). All India Survey on Higher Education 2013-14, GOI. Ministry of Human Resource Development of Higher Education. ND, India, p 19, retrieved on July 20, 2019 from <http://aishe.nic.in/home>
- [2] Annual Report (2008). Ministry of Human Resource Development, Department of Education, India.
- [3] Government of India (1966). Education and National Development. New Delhi, India: Ministry of Education.
- [4] National Development Council Document (2008): Planning Commission India.

IS THERE ANY GENDER DIFFERENCE IN PROBLEM SOLVING ABILITY IN MATHEMATICS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AFTER COVID PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Covid pandemic was one of the most challenging educational emergency occurred in our country. The educational challenges of school closure in Kerala was resisted by “First Bell” digital classes through VICTERS channel and Online supporting classes by Teachers .Covid pandemic changes the traditional class room teaching to the new online mode of teaching in secondary school. The school closure and online mode of teaching made a drastic change in the behaviour of our students .This study have been under taken to find out whether there exist any cognitive change in learners due to the impact of online mode of teaching in mathematics during covid pandemic and how it reflected gender wise in the problem solving ability in mathematics of secondary school students in Kerala. To improve the quality of education selection of suitable method of teaching is most important .To select the most suitable method for effective transaction of content. It is necessary to know the present status of our learners .After covid pandemic we can see an overall change in the nature and characteristics of our students .So it is significant to study whether there exist any gender difference in problem solving ability in mathematics among secondary school students after covid pandemic .The study was conducted in a sample of 100 secondary school students in Kozhikode district .survey method was adopted .Test of problem solving ability in mathematics (Aruna & Lisheetha ,2018) were used to collect data. The statistical technique used for analysis and interpretation of data were percentage analysis and test of significance of difference between means .The findings of the study revealed that there exist significant gender difference in problem solving ability in mathematics among secondary school students in Kerala.

The purpose of education one says ,is to form character ,another to prepare for complete living ;a third ,to produce a sound mind in sound body ;and the series of replies of this kind could easily be continued . All of them seem satisfactory until ,pursuing the matter farther ,we ask what kind of character it is desirable to form what activities complete living include or what are the marks of a healthy mind .We then find ,as M.W .Keatinge “Studies in Education (Black ,1916) has trenchantly pointed out ,that the success of these attempts to state a universal aim for education is largely illusory ,being due chiefly to the fact that every one may with in wide limlits ,interpret them just ‘as he pleases’. Every scheme of education being at bottom ,a practical philosophy necessarily touches life at every point .Hence any educational aims are concrete enough to ideals of life are eternally at variance their conflict will be reflected in educational theories.

Education through the process of socialization strengthens gendering practices in school .Education reproduces domestication through gendered socialization of girls and boys in school. mathematics, “the queen of all sciences” occupies a central place in school curriculum. The fundamental goals of all instruction is to develop skills, knowledge and abilities which transfer to tasks not given explicitly in the curriculum. Problem solving ability occupies a very important place in the teaching of Mathematics. The difference of Mathematics from other school subjects is lying here as it provide wide opportunity to solve problems these stimulate thinking ability of learners as well as teachers.

Mathematics has traditionally been regarded as white middle –class ,male territory ,and in many countries ,the lower status of females has been attributed to their lessor involvement and poorer performance in mathematics .To counter this situation, diverse programs and legislation have been introduced in recent decades to increase female participation rate and levels of achievement in mathematics .Not surprisingly ,these programs and the gender differences in mathematics learning they are designed to remedy have attracted much attention not only from practitioners and policy makers. Reports of mathematics performance across countries and across genders tend to rely heavily on results from a few large scale, comprehensive international studies .These reports often give limited attention to the relative unimportance of small between group differences or the complex conditions that help to produce those differences. Among the latter are the tests themselves , and recent research has shown that the direction and size of male-female differences in mathematics performance depends on the ways in which such performance is assessed.

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Difference in mathematics performance between males and females were rarely reported before students entered elementary school or during the early years of elementary school. However, from the beginning of secondary school and beyond, male often, but not unfailingly, outperformed females on tests in mathematics. Whether differences were found seemed to differ on the content of the tests, whether high or low cognitive level items predominated, and whether standardized test or class room based data were compared. These large scale testing reveal complex patterns of gender differences in mathematics performance, whether and by how much one group outperforms another seems to depend on attitudes, the age of the students, the type of mathematical items on which students are tested and the country in which testing takes place. This study has been undertaken to find out whether there exist any cognitive change in learners due to the impact of online mode of teaching in mathematics during covid pandemic and how it reflected gender wise in the problem solving ability in mathematics of secondary school students in Kerala.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives formulated for the present study. To find out the level of problem solving ability in mathematics among secondary school students in Kozhikode district. To find out whether there exist any significant difference in the mean scores of problem solving ability in mathematics between the sub samples boys and girls.

Hypotheses of the Study

The following are the hypotheses formulated for the present study. There will be significant difference in the mean scores of problem solving ability in mathematics between the sub samples boys and girls.

Methodology

In the present study, descriptive survey method is followed as it is the most appropriate method to know the present status. Sample of the Study: In the present research work, stratified random sampling technique was used by the investigators for the selection of the sample of 100 Secondary school students from Kozhikode district. Tools Used: In order to achieve the objectives of the study the investigator used – Test of problem solving ability in Mathematics for standard IX pupil (Aruna & Lisheetha, 2018). In the present test the items belonging to inductive reasoning, cause effect relationships and application are used. The investigator prepared a final test with 45 multiple choice items. The duration of the test was fixed for 45 minutes. Weightage to content was given for the selected topics. In order to ensure the validity of the Test of problem solving ability in Mathematics, the investigator used content validity. The Investigator used the test-retest method to find out the reliability of the test. Statistical Techniques Used: The collected data were analyzed by using; Preliminary tests (Mean, Median, Mode, Skewness and Kurtosis). Test of significance of difference between means to accept or reject the hypotheses.

Results and Discussion

Level of Problem Solving Ability in Mathematics of Secondary School Students

In this section the percentage of problem solving ability in Mathematics is found out for the total sample and are given in the table 1

Table 1. Details of Level of Problem Solving Ability in Mathematics among Secondary School Students for the Total Sample

Variable	Number of total students	Level of scores	Students number	% of students
Problemsolving ability in mathematics	100	Low	15	15%
		Average	67	67%
		High	18	18%

Table 1 shows that, for the total sample, 15% of students having low problem solving ability in Mathematics, 18% of students having high problem solving ability in mathematics. Then 67% of the students are having average problem solving ability in Mathematics.

Figure 1. The figure showing the level of problem solving ability in Mathematics.

Comparison of Mean Scores of Problem Solving ability in mathematics for the subsamples

As part of the analysis, the difference in the mean scores of problem solving ability in mathematics of secondary school students were found out .For this purpose problemsolving ability in mathematics of secondary school boys and girls are subjected to two tailed test of significance of difference between means and results were studied.

Table2 .The data and results of comparison of mean scores of problem solving ability in mathematics for the subsamples.

Variable	Subsamples	Number of samples	Mean	Standard Deviation	Critical Ratio
Problem solving ability in Mathematics	Boys	50	16.74	6.130586	3.206933**
	girls	50	18.22	4.554836	

** significant at 0.01 level

The above table reveals that the critical ratio obtained for the variable problem solving ability in Mathematics between girls and boys is 3.206933 which is greater than the table value 2.58 required for significance at 0.01 level. This shows that there is significant difference the problem solving ability of boys and girls . That means there exists gender difference in problem solving ability of students .High mean scores are associated with girls that means girls are higher in problemsolving ability in mathematics than boys.

Major Findings of the Study

There exist significant gender difference in problem solving ability in mathematics of secondary school students in Kerala. Girls are higher in problemsolving ability in Mathematics than boys.

Educational Implication of the Study

This study will be help full to select appropriate method for boys and girls for effective transaction of content. This study will be helpful to understand the learners ability to acquire and apply knowledge and skills and helpful for developing curriculum at secondary level. This study will be helpful for constructing new strategies and methods like blended learning classroom for effective transaction of content in mathematics.

References

- [1] Best, J.W., & Khan, J.V. (2008). *Research in education*, (10th ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd.
- [2] Blooms, B.S. (1956). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: Cognitive domain*. New York: David Mckay Publishing.

URBAN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education in urban area consists of dense cities with large population meanwhile, it can be referred to as a growing city. In this urban area, education can be very helpful in teaching learning in urban areas, there will be a higher enrolment of both teachers and students more practical problems are found in urban education urban education is characterized by inattentiveness of students and High dropout rate. This urban education is mainly initiated in the growing cities. Education is one of the most needed in such cities this education also requires more space. This urban education is started by knowing the causes of learning and understanding the needs and conditions of learning.

Keywords: *Education, Population, Growing City, Teaching Learning, Higher Enrolment, Urban Education*

Introduction

This urban pedagogy has teaching and learning at its core. Urban education provides an introduction to those in the area. It represents the hardships students in urban areas and the challenges they face on a daily basis. An urban area is considered to be the area surrounding that city only. These are also used to grow the people in that city.

Need of Urban Education

Education is important for everyone. All students know the importance of education. Our education is what defines us. This education is used to learn about the world. This education is also used to develop decision making and thinking skills. Education is also used to develop the skills we have. Education is something that can help in every way.

Importance of Urban Education

In urban areas this education is only useful for those urban students. This does not benefit the rural students. Urban students are more likely to have more opportunities and rural students cannot afford more. The gap between rural and urban areas is widening as urbanization continues to increase. Urbanization varies due to population growth, migration, relocation etc., Education is an important use in the growth of the economy.

Merits of Urban Education

- 1) Urban students get the opportunity to get better education.
- 2) They get better education than those in the village.
- 3) More varieties of food are available in urban areas than in rural areas.
- 4) School buses are available for going to schools and returning home after school.
- 5) Tools are also more available in urban schools.
- 6) Educational opportunities are more available in urban areas.
- 7) The recycling system is in store here.
- 8) Urban education brings us various facilities like internet facility.
- 9) Urban education creates job opportunity.
- 10) Education helps to solve our problem.
- 11) Urban education helps to achieve economic prosperity and increase the opportunity to discover new things.

Demerits of Urban Education

- 1) Living space is very less here.
- 2) No Street light.
- 3) Even the location is not well organized.

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- 4) There is a possibility of accumulation of garbage and waste, smog and facing financial crisis and economic problem.
- 5) The city is highly paid and competitive for location.
- 6) Food means lack of purity and absence of green leafy vegetables.
- 7) Population density tends to allow more social unrest in the densely populated areas, affecting people's lives.
- 8) Environmental damage leads to poor food habits and frequent infectious diseases.

Conclusion

Education is used to improve us and take us on the road to good progress. These lead to improve us from urban life.

Reference

- [1] <https://ischoolconnect.com>blog>
- [2] <https://tophat.com>
- [3] <https://www.insightsonindia.com>
- [4] <https://www.tandonline.com>
- [5] <https://habitatbroward.org>
- [6] <https://www.reportlinker.com>

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Inclusive education means that physically challenged and mentally retarded people are included in this education as well as those with good physical and mental strength and are taught the same subjects. Inclusive education enables students with disabilities to receive learning and teaching in the same classroom as normal students. Inclusive education is imparted to the extent that the same curriculum is learned together in the same classroom. The curriculum is presented to the students in a simple way through activities according to the ability of the students. Inclusive education helps students to work together in the same classroom without discrimination. Inclusive education is very helpful for students with disabilities to excel in the society as well as normal students. Through inclusive education students have been making and achieving many achievements over the years. This improves their quality of good life.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Physical And Mental Strength, Curriculum, Work Together*

Introduction

Inclusion is behaviour. It's recognising, valuing, and fully leveraging different perspectives and backgrounds to provide a positive work environment. In order to leverage diversity, an environment must be created where children always feel supported, listened to, and able to do their personal best.

Inclusion is Students with Disability

Attending the same schools as their siblings and neighbours. Being in general education classrooms with chronological age-appropriate classmates. Having individualized and relevant learning objectives. Being provided with the necessary support. Inclusive education is coming up with practices that allow each student feel respected, confident and safe so he/she can learn and develop his/her full potential. To be included is to be accepted and to be able to participate fully within our families, communities and society.

Principles of Inclusive Education

- 1) Increase participation of learners
- 2) Reducing exclusion
- 3) Flexible curriculum
- 4) Inclusive school culture
- 5) Policies and practices in promoting inclusion

Process of Inclusive Education

- 1) Acceptance
- 2) Understanding
- 3) Attending

Successful inclusive education happens primarily through accepting, understanding, attending to student differences and diversity, which can include physical, cognitive, academic, social and emotional.

UDL: Universal Design Learning

UDL is a flexible pedagogical framework that aims to remove barriers and increase accessibility for as many students as possible. A ramp allows anyone to enter a building, whereas a staircase allows only certain people to enter. Similarly, UDL asks us to abandon "one size fits all" thinking in order to create curriculum designs that are inclusive of all students. Within the three major components of curriculum design and implementation, UDL focuses on increasing flexibility, choice, and relevance.

Conclusion

Inclusion is about personalising education so that everyone succeeds, regardless of their unique needs, and implementing an equity-based mindset is sometimes the best way to ensure that occurs.

Reference

- [1] <https://oaipplus.pdx.edu/introduction-to-universal-design-for-learning/>
- [2] <https://inclusiveeducation.ca/about/what-is-ie/>

SOCIAL WELFARE SCHMES AND THEIR IMPACT ON STUDENTS FOR BETTER LEARNING: GENDER AND LOCALITY

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Abstract

Welfare refers to a range of government programs that provide financial or other aid to individuals or groups who cannot support themselves. Welfare programs are typically funded by taxpayers and allow people to cope with financial stress during rough periods of their lives. In most cases, people who use welfare will receive a biweekly or monthly payment. The goals of welfare vary, as it looks to promote the pursuance of work, education, or, in some instances, a better standard of living. So an investigation is made by the researcher on social welfare schemes and their impact on students for better learning by taking independent variable gender and locality. The tool is standardized by item analysis. A stratified random sampling method is used for a sample of 630 students from different high schools. The data is collected by survey cum interview method in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. Mean, SD, t test and f-ratio statistical technique are used at 0.05 and 0.01 level. It is found that There is no significant difference between boys and girls in utility of nadu nedu, ammavadi, Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka, Jagan Gorumudda and Badiki Vasta social welfare schmes in Kurnool district, but there isa significant difference between urban and rural students in utility of nadu nedu, ammavadi, Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka, Jagan Gorumudda and Badiki Vasta social welfare schmes in Kurnool district.

Introduction

Welfare, or more frequently social welfare, is a form of government aid aimed at ensuring that citizens can satisfy essential requirements like food and housing (Encyclopedia Britannica). As an alternative to social assistance programs that only provide support based on need, social security may be used to refer to social insurance programs that only provide support to those who have previously contributed (such as most pension systems), or it may specifically refer to these programs (e.g. most disability benefits). According to the International Labor Organization, social security includes payments for the elderly, the maintenance of children, medical care, parental and sick leave, unemployment and disability insurance, and assistance for people who have sustained industrial harm (Frans Pennings, 2006). In a broader sense, welfare may also refer to initiatives to promote a minimal degree of well-being through free or heavily discounted social services such as public housing, healthcare, education, and training programs (The New Fontana Dictionary of Modern Thought Third Edition, 1999). In a welfare state, the government is in charge of ensuring the well-being of the populace and ensuring that everyone has access to social services like those listed above (Vrooman 2009). In the present study the investigator made a investigation on social welfare schmes and their impact on students for better learning: gender and locality.

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy.

Fig. Sample Design

Tool

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the utility of social welfare schemes in Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the utility level of social welfare scheme by Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.
- 2) To find out the utility level of social welfare scheme by urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district

Hypothesis

- 1) There would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme by Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.
- 2) There would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme by urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district

Fig 2. Utility of social welfare schemes by high school students according to their Gender. and locality

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Table 1: Means, SD's and t- values of utility of social welfare scmes by high school students according to their Gender.

S.No	Scheme	Gender	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Nadu-Nedu	Boys	320	85.12	9.47	0.9011@
		Girls	310	85.75	8.04	
2	Amma Vadi	Boys	320	83.11	10.30	0.2841@
		Girls	310	83.33	9.04	
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	Boys	320	100.52	9.99	1.3966@
		Girls	310	101.67	10.65	
4	Jagan Gorumudda	Boys	320	58.90	7.86	1.3764@
		Girls	310	59.77	8.00	
5	Badiki Vasta	Boys	320	52.01	6.82	1.1065@
		Girls	310	52.57	5.86	
6	Over All	Boys	320	379.67	33.33	1.3488@
		Girls	310	383.10	30.47	

Note:

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The utility levels of social welfare scheme boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool districted are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 320 and 310. The total no of students are 630, as shown in figure 1 and table 4.2 . In nadu nedu scheme the mean and SD values of boys are 85.12 and 9.47, similarly the girls are 85.7 and 8.04. The nean values of girls are slightly high in comparision to boys. The t value is 0.9011, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In amma vadi scheme the mean and SD values of boys are 85.75 and 10.30 , similarly the girls are 83.11 and 9.04. The nean values of boys are slightly high in comparision to girls . The t value is 0.2841, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In Jagananna vidya kanuka scheme the mean and SD values of boys are 100.52 and 8.99, similarly the girls are 101.67 and 10.65 The nean values of girls are slightly high in comparision to boys. he t value is 1.3966, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In Jafananna gorumudda the mean and SD values of boys are 58.90and 7.86, similarly the girls are 59.77 and 8.00. The nean values of girls are slightly high in comparision to boys. The t value is 1.3764, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In badiki vasta scheme the mean and SD values of boys are 52.01 and 6.82 , similarly the girls are 52.57 and 5.86 . The nean values of girls are slightly high in comparision to boys. The t value is 1.1065, which is not significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In over all the mean and SD values of boys are 379.67 and 33.33, similarly the girls are 380.10 and 30.47. The nean values of girls are slightly high in comparision to boys. The t value is 1.3488,

Fig 3. Mean and SD'values of utility of social welfare scmes by high school students according to their Gender.

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Table 2: Means, SD's and t- values of utility of social welfare schemes by high school students according to their Locality

S.No	Scheme	Locality	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Nadu-Nedu	Urban	296	87.04	6.33	4.4438**
		Rural	334	84.00	10.30	
2	Amma Vadi	Urban	296	86.48	7.44	8.3458**
		Rural	334	80.31	10.54	
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	Urban	296	104.72	8.22	8.9677**
		Rural	334	97.86	10.92	
4	Jagan Gorumudda	Urban	296	60.62	7.45	3.9176**
		Rural	334	58.18	8.18	
5	Badiki Vasta	Urban	296	54.29	6.07	8.4689**
		Rural	334	50.51	6.09	
6	Over All	Urban	296	393.17	21.35	9.5818**
		Rural	334	370.88	35.96	

Note:

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The utility level of social welfare scheme of urban and rural students are interpreted as follows and the sample size of urban students are 296 and rural students are 334. In nadu nedu scheme the the mean value as shown in table 4.4 and in figure 4.3 the of urban students more than that of rural students. The t value is 4.4438, which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of nadu nedu scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. In amma vadi scheme the the mean value of urban students more than that of rural students. As shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The t value is, 8.3458 which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of amma vadi scheme by high school students of Kurnool district.

In Jagananna vidya kanuka scheme the the mean value of urban students more than that of rural students. As shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The t value is, 8.9677 which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna vidya kanuka scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. In Jagananna goru muda scheme the the mean value of urban students more than that of rural students. As shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The t value is, 3.9176 which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna goru muda scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. In Badiki Vasta scheme the the mean value of urban students more than that of rural students. As shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The t value is, 8.4689 which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Badiki Vasta scheme by high school students of Kurnool district.

In Over all scheme the the mean value of urban students more than that of rural students. As shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The t value is, 9.5818 which is significant at 0.01. There is a significant difference between urban and rural students in utilizing social welfare schemes. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Overall scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. The utility level of social welfare scheme of urban and rural students, the sample size of urban students are 296 and rural students are 334. It is found that There fore it is found that

there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of nadu nedu schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of amma vadi schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna vidya kanuka schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There fore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna goru muda scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Badiki Vasta scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Overall scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that the uthere is a significant difference in utility level of social welfare scheme of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district. The urban student utilizing all the schemes better than rural high school students of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh.

Fig 4.3. Mean and SD values of utility of social welfare scmes by high school students according to their Locality

Conclusions

There is no significant difference between boys and girls in utility of nadu nedu, amnavadi, Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka, Jagan Gorumudda and Badiki Vasta social welfare schmes in Kurnool district. The utility level of social welfare scheme of urban and rural students, the sample size of urban students are 296 and rural students are 334. It is found that There fore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of nadu nedu schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of amma vadi schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna vidya kanuka schme by high school students of Kurnool district. There fore it is found that there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Jagananna goru muda scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. there is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Badiki Vasta scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. There is a significant difference among urban and rural students in utility of Overall scheme by high school students of Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that the uthere is a significant difference in utility level of social welfare scheme of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district. The urban student utilizing all the schemes better than rural high school students of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh.

References

- [1] Frans Pennings (2006). Between Soft and Hard Law: The Impact of International Social Security Standards on National Social Security Law. Kluwer Law International B.V. pp. 32–41. ISBN 978-90-411-2491-3.
- [2] The New Fontana Dictionary of Modern Thought Third Edition (1999), Allan Bullock and Stephen Trombley Eds., p. 919..
- [3] Vrooman, J.C. (2009). Rules of Relief: Institutions of Social Security, and Their Impact (PDF). Netherlands Institute for Social Research, SCP. pp. 111–126

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract

This paper provides an overview of the professional education and development opportunities available to biology teachers. It examines the various models of professional development, including mentoring, collaborating, and self-directed learning, as well as the challenges faced by biology teachers in acquiring professional development. It further discusses the benefits of professional development for both teachers and students, including improved student learning, increased teacher satisfaction and confidence, and the potential to lead to greater career advancement. Finally, the abstract outlines the resources available to biology teachers to access professional development opportunities.

Keywords: *Professional Education, Professional Development, Biology Teacher, Importance*

Professional Education

Professional education played a very important role worldwide in the last decades of the twentieth century. The scientific and technical revolution of the 1970s created new demands for scientists and engineers, and noticeably increased the quantity of information that students of universities had to study. The rapid development of technology led to the differentiation of knowledge and made professional training more specialized. Once differentiated by this training, graduates were not able to study new fields of science and use the achievements of allied sciences. The system of professional education started to conflict with the demands of economic and technical development. This led to significant changes in the system of professional education in several industrialized countries in the 1970s.

The other reason for changes in professional education in the 1990s changed the social and political systems of many countries. Political changes brought changing viewpoints on education and its role in society. For a long time in many countries, education had been viewed as an instrument of the state for forming a specific type of person for society. The role of education was reduced to training personnel for science, industry, agriculture, and the everyday activities of a country. This point of view saw the development principally of technical specialties in higher education and a rapid increase in professional secondary school at the expense of general secondary school. In recent years, the symbiosis between education and culture has become clear. The understanding of this interdependence has seen a change in the system of professional education, with a reduction in technical education at all levels and a rapid increase in humanities fields of professional education.

However, this has led to substantial differences in the content of professional training and variations in different countries. Professional education can be defined in different ways. It can be defined by the goal of education. In this definition, professional education would be the education of different levels utilizing which people qualify for a certain profession or specialty. On the other hand, professional education can be defined by the type of educational institution: this would be the education obtained in professional secondary schools, universities, and institutes. The type of professional education that is established, the duration of the training, and the degrees obtained depend on the system of education in each country. The systems of education in different countries are quite different, but they can be reduced to some main types. The professions (or specialties) they qualify graduates for are defined by the structure of education, which is also different in each country. The structure of education defines the distribution of students and graduates in various fields.

The International Standard Classification of Education (ISCE) defines the following fields of education:

- 1) Education: pedagogical sciences and training of teachers.
- 2) Humanities: arts; religion.
- 3) Law and social sciences: Law and Social Sciences; Commercial and Business Management; Communication and Documentation; Domestic Science.
- 4) Natural, technical, and agricultural sciences: Natural Sciences; Technical Sciences; Mathematics And Informatics; Architecture And Civil Construction; Transport And Communication; Industry; Trade And Handicraft; Agriculture, Forest Industry, And Fishing.
- 5) Medical Sciences: Medicine and Public Health Sciences.

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Importance of Professional Education

Professional education is important because it prepares individuals for a successful career. Professional education helps develop both the technical and soft skills necessary to excel in a chosen field. Technical skills are those skills required to perform a certain job or task, while soft skills are those interpersonal skills that are necessary for effective communication and collaboration. Professional education also provides individuals with the tools they need to make sound decisions in the workplace, develop their leadership skills, and stay up to date on industry trends. Additionally, professional education gives individuals the opportunity to network and build professional relationships, which can be beneficial to both their career and long-term success.

Professional Development Of Biology Teachers

Biology Teacher The quality, competence, and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant in the different factors which influence the quality of education and its contribution to national development. Nothing is more important than securing a sufficient supply of high-quality recruits for the teaching of science, providing them with the best possible professional preparation, and creating satisfactory conditions of work in which they can be fully effective. Pupils pay more attention to new, noble, and latest knowledge rather than only bookish knowledge.

A Good Biology Teacher

- 1) Selects important principles and facts from the entire syllabus and presents them in front of his/her students in a collective manner using the appropriate method.
- 2) Is familiar with the techniques of evaluation to evaluate his/her students correctly.
- 3) Makes his/her teaching successful through a knowledge acquisition process by obtaining complete knowledge of the personal needs, understanding capacity, and problems of the students.
- 4) Is fully competent in selecting 'Biology Apparatus' and making proper use of it.
- 5) Provides systematic instructions to his/her students. Students take part in all instructional activities.
- 6) Is an expert in organizing exhibitions, science fairs, and other activities for the people of the school and community?
- 7) Gives introduction of his/her capabilities in the laboratory, work sphere, and school community and helps others.
- 8) Is proud to be a teacher. To improve his/her teaching skills, students take part in various conventions, clubs, scientific group activities, and in-service teaching experiments/research. In this way, students are always aware of his/her responsibilities.

Professional Ability of Biology Teacher

- 1) Participating in community workshops, in-service training courses, workshops, meetings, conferences, etc.
- 2) Having information on various new research developments.
- 3) Subscribing to good books, magazines, bulletins, and newspapers for the library and studying them.
- 4) Listening to and watching various programs based on science on the radio and TV.
- 5) Participating in the activities of occupational organizations of science teaching.
- 6) Having good knowledge of other schools, colleges, universities, research institutes, and regional laboratories and acquiring knowledge.
- 7) Taking part in the local, regional, and national meetings.
- 8) Acquiring knowledge of good teaching methods of science at the national level.
- 9) Participating in meetings of the committee preparing Instructional Material.

Aware of the new facts/happenings and the latest information, which students will be able to impart to the students.

Professional Competencies of Biology Teachers

Biology teachers are skilled educators who teach students various concepts of biological sciences while preparing their course curriculum. They work in schools and other educational institutions and deliver lectures while performing tasks such as lesson planning and conducting skill assessment tests. Their enthusiasm and knowledge of the subject help them perform their various job duties effectively. In this article, we explore the answer to "what does a biology teacher do," along with helpful job skills and duties they perform to educate the students.

Success of educational plans in each country depends on the teachers armed with scientific competencies and professional skills. Researchers in education have done many researches to find out the competencies of a good teacher and an impressive teaching and have divided those competencies into different categories, but these researches have not been coherent and practical. Each of these categories considers a specific aspect and we explore three of them in here. Fathivajargah (2003) believes that when we are hiring teachers, we must hire those who have cognitive, emotional and practical competencies. Cognitive competency here means self- cognition, learners-cognition, and cognition of teaching-learning process. Emotional competency is the competence based on interests, values and attitudes. And practical competency refers to teacher's competence in relation with the students, classrooms, schools and the society.

Bloom imprecisely divides teachers' competencies to emotional, cognitive and practical (quoting Seif, 2003). Aghaie (2006) thinks that the most important competencies of a teacher are:

- 1) Familiarity with different thinking skills and applying them.
- 2) Familiarity with new learning and teaching methods and using them
- 3) Class management and specific skills of communicating with the students
- 4) Familiarity with communication and information technologies, and is capable of employing them in teaching
- 5) Research skills
- 6) Skillful in evaluating academic achievements

Shabani (2006) also divides teachers' competencies into characteristic and scientific. By characteristic competencies he means: student-oriented authoritarian, student-oriented and intimacy-oriented, subject-oriented and intimacy oriented, and subject-oriented authoritarian; By scientific competencies, he means: awareness of psychology, teaching methods, new communication methods, social psychology, teaching psychology, and communicating. Taghi Pour Zahir (2010) divides teachers' competencies into two categories; vocational and personal. Personal competencies include: mental and physical health, adherence to values, and having good mental abilities, and vocational competencies include: general knowledge, vocational knowledge, and communication skills. The general competencies of a teacher include familiarity with development and learning psychology, awareness of the teaching-learning process, class management, teaching methods, controlling, and evaluation. Specialized competencies of a teacher in this research include: content mastery, providing the content in proper order, organizing the content, mastery in employing training tools in practice, keeping accurate records, and giving feedback to the students. If teachers have professional competencies, they will regard the following points:

- 1) Emphasis on human relationships and cooperation in improving the learning conditions
- 2) More emphasis on the consequences of learning than on its products
- 3) Emphasis on learners' self-evaluation, and their responsibility for their learning and also other students' learning
- 4) Making opportunities for internal motivation development

- 5) Increasing judgmental sources and data validity
- 6) Giving descriptive feedback to bring improvement and performance development
- 7) Modulation of evaluation system with the social system of school

Conclusion

The professional education and development of biology teachers are essential for inspiring the next generation of scientists and promoting a greater understanding of the world around us. By providing teachers with the necessary skills, resources, and support, they can effectively engage their students to develop a deeper appreciation and understanding of biology. This in turn helps to ensure students are better prepared to tackle the challenges of the modern world and make a positive contribution to society.

References

- [1] Aghaie, Ali (2006). Recognition of Personal and Professional Features of Future Teachers. MA thesis, Tehran: Shahed University.
- [2] Chikkara & Sharma -Teaching of Biology, Tandon Publication Ludhiana
- [3] R.C. Sharma, Modern Science Teaching, Dhanpat Rai Publishing company-pg 248-257
- [4] Shabani, Hsan(2006). Educational Skills. Tehran: Samt.

LIFE SKILLS PERTAINING TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Inclusive education in the education system of world is the Key word in the 21st century. Considering the varied ability of students learning in any classroom of the world is a character of a classroom. Life skills in the classroom of varied ability students will be successful and effective is a challenge before today's education system. The understanding of the basic principles of inclusive education motivates the inclusion of children with special needs in general education schools. The paper presents the process of life skills concerning inclusive education mainly understanding the role of communication in including children with special needs, communication strategies, basic qualities, and their use in teachers' work with children with special needs. As they are the important building blocks for a dynamic citizen, who can cope with future challenges, and survive well.

Keywords: *Life Skills, Inclusive Education.*

Introduction

The term 'Life Skills' refers to the skills you need to make the most out of life. Any skill that is useful in your life can be considered a life skill. It is an art of living, which helps us to draw a personal and professional sketch of life. It enables individuals with difficulties to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. In life-skills education, the student is taught to develop a sense of his or her worth and dignity as a person. Here in this paper it mainly focus on communication skills concerning Inclusive education. The inclusion of students with the most significant cognitive disabilities in general education classrooms with typical peers, research has found that the majority of these students spend the largest part of their school day in self-contained classrooms or separate schools (Kleinert et al., 2015). They often have complex communication needs, with limited receptive and expressive communication skills. A lack of communicative competence, defined broadly, is a major factor working against full inclusion for these students in the general education classroom and curriculum. In addition, limited communication skills can also exclude students from participating in social interactions with typical peers.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education refers to a concept of inclusion that is “based on the notion that schools should, without question, provide for the needs of all the children in their communities, whatever the level of their ability or disability”. - (Foreman, 2011, pg. 548). Inclusive education requires that schools should be free from the effect of negative forms of discrimination based on gender, Disability, culture, ethnicity, Religion or differences arising from students' socioeconomic and or geographic backgrounds (UNESCO, 1994). .However, it is still reported that educators are facing most discomfort & lack of confidence in including children with special needs in their programs. Inclusive education aims to high quality teaching & Learning. As a result of such changes in education sectors, classroom are welcoming diverse learners who were previously segregated & this situation is Creating more challenges for educators to meet every child learning needs.

Life Skills And Inclusive Education

Life skills focus on the development of intellectual, mental, physical, emotional, and social abilities. Children need these Life skills to achieve goals, especially in a world filled with distractions and information overload. This includes paying attention, exercising self-control, remembering the rules and thinking flexibly. Much more than understanding language, reading, writing and speaking, communicating is the skill of determining what one wants to communicate and realizing how it will be understood by others. It is the skill teachers and employers feel is most lacking today. Children with special needs, in spite of their emotional, social, cognitive or physical problems, study together with children without such problems and get an opportunity to obtain skills for a successful and independent life in society. The division of educational institutions into comprehensive and special schools shows an unequal approach to children with special needs (Yanson, 2008). Children with special needs succeed better both academically and socially if they work in an integrated setting (Lebeer, 2006). The process of

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life skills concerning inclusive education mainly understanding the role of communication in including children with special needs, communication strategies, basic qualities, and their use in teachers' work with children with special needs.

1. Personal care

Nutrition education and a balanced diet are important for students with special needs. Assist them in developing regular personal hygiene habits. Discuss how you can treat illnesses and fevers such as allergies and the common cold with them. Make them presentable by getting dressed and getting ready. Visual schedules can help with routines.

2. Essential Math

Encourage children to make a personal budget, count money, make correct change, tell the time, and manage their finances. Explain the importance of good spending habits and saving. Teach them how to manage their bank accounts and keep track of their transactions.

3. Household Skills

In addition to learning how to maintain the safety of a house, people with special needs can also learn how to get their house repaired and how to service the heating/cooling system, and other appliances if necessary. They can also learn how to store food properly, check the expiration dates on meat, canned food, and other edible items, and how to clean the house.

4. Essential Reading

Since the internet has become an indispensable part of our lives, people with special needs can be taught how to use search engines to look up information. They can also be trained to read maps and signs, so that they can travel within the community by themselves. They can also learn to read and understand important documents.

5. Leisure and Recreation

Every individual should be encouraged to pursue their passions and develop their talents. Even as you teach them important job skills, you can also guide them to participate in social events. Whether they like music or movies, they can learn how to get access to their favorite form of entertainment. They can also be taught about how to plan and enjoy vacations.

6. Community Living

Focus on giving them an education that imparts knowledge of citizens' rights, the law, and how to abide by it. Teach them how to report a crime, get emergency care for themselves or those around them, and get legal aid. You can use social stories to explain how to be a responsible citizen and follow the rules. Encourage them to observe political developments and exercise their right to vote.

7. Safety

Teach students with disabilities about safety signs and their meanings. They should be aware of fire and other safety hazards, and ways to get themselves to safety in case of an accident. In the event of building evacuation, they should be aware of the exit pathways.

8. Self-Awareness and Self-Confidence

Children with special needs should be able to identify their emotional, physical, and psychological needs. Encourage them to acknowledge and receive praise and criticism. Focus on developing their sense of self-esteem.

9. Occupation Skills

Schools should prepare them to look for job opportunities and recognize the requirements of each job. They can be taught about the need for financial independence and the value of having an occupation. Teach students with disabilities about expectations in a work environment and how to adapt to work demands. They can

also be taught how to be professional at the workplace. They can be coached to follow directions and how to work as a team. They must be ready to accept supervision and be aware of safety procedures. Teach them about the importance of attendance and maintaining performance standards. Pre-vocational training should be part of their curriculum and opportunities must be created for simulating work experiences in the school. They should also receive vocational training and on-the-job training depending on their specific abilities. Parents of children with special needs dedicate a huge amount of their time and energy doing their best for the children. But the most precious gift they can give their children, and themselves, is their children's self-dependence. So, they must actively supplement the skills training received from school. They should consistently motivate their children to do everyday activities with little or no assistance. Such an approach will impress the merits of being independent upon them.

Conclusion

Communication problems create the need to establish a communicative approach model to work with children with special needs. Because children with special needs attend schools, the teacher must take responsibility and accept applying principles of inclusive education. The teacher's potential is essential as the teacher needs to be ready to work with children with special needs. Although inclusion is concerned with the quality of experiences of students with learning disabilities, such an approach benefits society as a whole. The inclusive environment allows students with learning disabilities to integrate into society and improves the quality of education.

Reference

- [1] UNESCO (1996). Resource teacher Education Resource Pack: Special Needs in the Classroom. UNESCO, Paris.
- [2] University of Melbourne (2005). Strategies for Inclusive Communication: Interacting with People with a Disability. Accessed on 12 November 2014. Retrieved from <https://www.unimelb.edu.au/diversity/downloads/communication.pdf>
- [3] Light, J. (1989). Toward a definition of communicative competence for individuals using augmentative and alternative communication systems. *Augmentative and Alternative Communication*, 5, 137–144.
- [4] Hocog I., R. and Quigley, M. A. (1995). Research Review for Inclusive Practices. Pacific Region Educational Laboratory,1-7.
- [5] Yanson, U. (2008). Исследование ситуации в области включенного обучения. [Research on the situation in the field of inclusive education]. St. Petersburg: Soobshestvo.
- [6] Lebeer, J. (Ed.) (2006). In-clues. Clues to inclusive and cognitive education. Antwerpen: Apeldoorn Garant Publishers.
- [7] <https://avazapp.com/blog/9-essential-life-skills-for-special-needs-children/>

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DIMENSIONS AND BENEFITS OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract

Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. At the classroom level, for example, teachers may modify or incorporate lessons to reflect the cultural diversity of the students in a particular class. In many cases, “culture” is defined in the broadest possible sense, encompassing race, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, and exceptionality a term applied to students with specialized needs or disabilities. Multicultural education tries to create equal educational opportunities for all students by changing the total school environment so that it will reflect the diverse cultures and groups within a society and within the nation's classrooms. There are five dimensions of multicultural education, they are Content integration, Knowledge construction process, Prejudice reduction, equity pedagogy, empowering school culture and social structure. To implement multicultural education effectively, teachers and administrators must attend to each of the five dimensions of multicultural education. Multicultural education helps all students see themselves in the curriculum and the classroom. It is a field of study that embraces techniques to advance and advocate educational equity for all students of every age. “It helps all students acquire the knowledge, skills, attributes, and attitudes needed to function in a democratic society while feeling valued and heard,” Howell said. The nation is enriched by the ethnic, cultural and language diversity among its citizens and within schools. Schools must find the ways to respect the diversity of their students as well as help to create an unified nation ,state to which all of the nations citizens have allegiance.

Introduction

Multicultural education is referred to as a modern and advanced teaching model which focuses on fostering principles of equality among all students in spite of their varied races, backgrounds, cultures, beliefs, and ethnicities. Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. At the classroom level, for example, teachers may modify or incorporate lessons to reflect the cultural diversity of the students in a particular class. In many cases, “culture” is defined in the broadest possible sense, encompassing race, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, and exceptionality a term applied to students with specialized needs or disabilities. It helps in integrating histories, values, and different viewpoints of all student groups in a class. From social skills & language barriers, classroom involvement to academic performance, and behavior to discipline, multicultural forms of education help in providing equitable academic opportunities to all students. Moreover, it helps in guiding an educator to remove barriers experienced in a multicultural class. Multicultural education tries to create equal educational opportunities for all students by changing the total school environment so that it will reflect the diverse cultures and groups within a society and within the nation's classrooms. Multicultural education is a process because its goals are ideals that teachers and administrators should constantly strive to achieve.

Dimensions of Multicultural Education

There are five dimensions of multicultural education. They are: Content integration: Content integration deals with the extent to which teachers use examples and content from a variety of cultures and groups to illustrate key concepts, generalizations, and issues within their subject areas or disciplines. Knowledge construction process: describes how teachers help students to understand, investigate, and determine how the biases, frames of reference, and perspectives within a discipline influence the ways in which knowledge is constructed within it. Students also learn how to build knowledge themselves in this dimension. Prejudice reduction: it describes lessons and activities used by teachers to help students to develop positive attitudes toward different racial, ethnic, and cultural groups. Research indicates that lessons, units, and teaching materials that include content about different racial and ethnic groups can help students to develop more positive intergroup attitudes if certain conditions exist in the teaching situation. These conditions include positive images of the ethnic

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groups in the materials and the use of multiethnic materials in a consistent and sequential way. Equity pedagogy: exists when teachers modify their teaching in ways that will facilitate the academic achievement of students from diverse racial, cultural, and social-class groups. The students from different racial and ethnic groups must feel that they have equal status in intergroup interactions, teachers and administrators must value and support cross-racial interactions, and students from different racial groups must work together in teams to pursue common goals. Empowering school culture and social structure : It is created when the culture and organization of the school are transformed in ways that enable students from diverse racial, ethnic, and gender groups to experience equality and equal status. The implementation of this dimension requires that the total environment of the school be reformed, including the attitudes, beliefs, and action of teachers and administrators, the curriculum and course of study, assessment and testing procedures, and the styles and strategies used by teachers. To implement multicultural education effectively, teachers and administrators must attend to each of the five dimensions of multicultural education described above. They should use content from diverse groups when teaching concepts and skills, help students to understand how knowledge in the various disciplines is constructed, help students to develop positive intergroup attitudes and behaviors, and modify their teaching strategies so that students from different racial, cultural, and social-class groups will experience equal educational opportunities. The total environment and culture of the school must also be transformed so that students from diverse ethnic and cultural groups will experience equal status in the culture and life of the school. Although the five dimensions of multicultural education are highly interrelated, each requires deliberate attention and focus.

Ways to Implement Multicultural Education in the Classroom

Understand Your Students: The most fundamental step is to understand the cultural and ethnic backgrounds of all the students. It can be achieved by going through their personal records, by interviewing them on the first day of the lecture, and by asking their previous teacher about the student. **Identifying their Strengths and weaknesses:** It is an teacher's responsibility to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the students to eliminate them, and improve their learning outcome. This can be achieved by checking previous academic records and regularly assessing the student's performance in the class.

Benefits of Multicultural Education

Students in multicultural educational environments can learn how to value all backgrounds and cultures. If students from a tender age can be comfortable with cultural differences, they are less likely to develop biases toward people of a different ethnicity or race . It Exposes Students to Various Cultures, Encourage acceptance among students, Helps to understand common problem, Helps in Building an International Network, Builds critical thinking ability. Students who learn about different cultures during their education feel more comfortable and safe with these differences later in life. This allows them to interact in a wider range of social groups and feel more confident in themselves as well as in their interactions with others. Multicultural learning can be used as a tool to open students' minds.

Conclusion

Multicultural education helps all students see themselves in the curriculum and the classroom. It is a field of study that embraces techniques to advance and advocate educational equity for all students of every age. "It helps all students acquire the knowledge, skills, attributes, and attitudes needed to function in a democratic society while feeling valued and heard," Howell said. The nation is enriched by the ethnic, cultural and language diversity among its citizens and within schools. Schools must find the ways to respect the diversity of their students as well as help to create an unified nation ,state to which all of the nations citizens have allegiance.

Reference

- [1] <https://onlinegrad.baylor.edu/resources/multicultural-education-strategies/>
- [2] <https://www.edglossary.org/multicultural-education/>
- [3] <https://www.iitms.co.in/blog/what-is-multicultural-education.html>
- [4] <https://poppylifecare.com/mindfulness-and-meditation/>

PHYSICAL EDUCATION - A PRIMARY TOOL FOR HOLISTIC LEARNING

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Abstract

Physical Education and Physical activities enhance the process of learning and development of the whole person, mind, body and soul. A meaningful plan of physical activities can become a motivational factor for all pupils, especially when their needs and benefits are well- understood. Therefore, classes in physical activities should among other things contain play, partnership, and rhythmical experiences with or without music in order to stimulate children's interest and concentration. This paper focuses on importance of physical education in holistic learning and its benefits. It develops interpersonal skills of the students like teamwork, leadership, communication, etc. and helps students combat mental health issues like stress and anxiety. It also builds resilience and emotional stability. Physical Education teachers, teaches lesson which gives students characteristics such as acting together, motivating friends, fair play, helping friends, responsibility, feeling comfortable and free, respecting others' rights and equality. In addition, teachers consider their lesson more prioritizes Physical Education curriculum than the other curriculum subjects, and they advocate that values are taught within hidden curriculum, though not directly.

Keywords: *Physical Education, Holistic Learning, Moral Values, Emotional and Physical Well-being.*

Introduction

Holistic education prepares a student for lifelong learning. The education focus moves towards the life skills, attitudes and personal awareness that the student will need in an increasingly complex world (Hare.J,2022). Students are taught to reflect their actions and how they impact the global and local community, as well as how to learn from the community around them. Teachers often engage students in projects that apply critical-thinking skills toward solving real-world problems. Holistic education is a comprehensive approach to teach where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. Emphasis is placed on positive school environments and providing whole-child supports (services that support academic and non-academic needs, also known as wraparound supports) to students. A longstanding evidence base exists on the multiple benefits of physical education (PE)for child and youth development (Bailey,2018). There is consensus that PE encompasses objectives in physical-motor and socio-emotional outcome domains, even though cross-country differences exist in the prioritization of aims and objectives of current PE curricula (Naul,2020). Increasing attention to PE outcomes in the motor domain has been attracted by the flourishing of research on the development of motor competence—that is the ability to perform goal-directed movements—and its predictive value for positive trajectories of physical health (Robinson,2015 & Barnett 2021) and cognitive development (Van,2015). Physical Education and Physical activities enhance the process of learning and development of the whole person, mind, body and soul. A meaningful plan of physical activities can become a motivational factor for all pupils, especially when their needs and benefits are well- understood. Therefore, classes in physical activities should among other things contain play, partnership, and rhythmical experiences with or without music in order to stimulate children's interest and concentration. This study intends to briefly explain the importance and benefits of holistic education through physical education.

Traditional Holistic Learning

Experiential Learning: Schools focused on experiential learning and provides hands-on educational experiences. For instance, students might work in groups exploring different learning styles to determine which styles are most effective for them. Holistic, experiential techniques often include problem-solving exercises to address community problems or create innovative products.

Self-Guided Learning: In self-guided educational environments, teachers allow students to learn at their own pace in the style that best suits them. The self-guided culture allows for personalization to mitigate the inadequacies of one-size-fits-all learning models. Low-stakes assessments are used to adjust the curriculum's content and pace. Classrooms may be smaller and contain students of different ages and ability levels.

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Community Schools: Community schools are based on the idea that people find meaning through connections with their community. Teachers partner with community members, including families, residents, organizations, and officials, to provide integrated support and expanded learning opportunities, including after-school and summer programs. Schools are a hub of the community bringing together academic, social, development, and engagement activities.

Interdisciplinary Coursework: Part of what makes up holistic education is the idea that students' cognitive growth is improved when multiple subjects are addressed together. Some schools are creating integrated programs where teachers from different disciplines come together to teach thematic courses that address issues from multiple perspectives. Coursework might also include independent research, travel, fieldwork, and internships.

Physical Education and Holistic Learning

Physical Education and Physical well-being: Up keeping one's physical fitness is a key component of ensuring a healthy lifestyle. This is why Physical education is introduced as a key subject in the curriculum of leading universities over the world. It has been cognized through research that inculcating fitness activities in one's timetable, help not only improve cardiovascular health but also develop muscle strength. This, in turn, also effectuates healthy lifestyle habits. Well-being improves students' academic performance, behaviour, social integration, and satisfaction. Wellbeing improves teachers' ability to interact with students, teach concepts, face challenges, and avoid burnout.

Physical Education and Emotional well-being: Yet another factor that finds a place in the Physical education curriculum is emotional wellbeing. This aspect helps students in knowing themselves and enables them to face the problems that life throws at them. This element focuses on multiple concepts like a cognitive appraisal, action, physiological change, and neurobiological explanation. The psychomotor domain refers to physical activity –related to mental process and also addresses the development of movement skills, the protection of health and the enhancement of performance levels in relation to several kinds of physical activity and the motivation of being active physically.

Physical Education and Social well-being: Physical education classes are not restricted to merely exercises, it also ensures to upkeep the social well-being of the students. This is to say that the physical education curriculum makes sure that students have a healthy relationship with their family, peers, and teachers. This is attained through team games, friendly matches, and multiple other activities. Communication is based on the interaction of two or more individuals in a verbal or non-verbal ways with gestures, movements and facial expressions as long as the codes, signals and/or symbols are common and can be understood by those who communicate. Through communication, people can share thoughts, ideas, feelings, opinions etc. Additionally, it helps children to be confident and engaged socially.

Physical Education and Intellectual well-being: Not all children express themselves in the same way, learn and develop in the same way and within the same pace, or share the same interests with others. Something, which can be interesting and attractive for one child, can be stressful and/or indifferent for some other. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is not always related to the personal interest of the child in the subject and may not even be related to the subject itself. A practical example is when children are given a reward or a grade as a motive for participation in some activity, it can also describe it as external motivation. The cognitive domain addresses the function of processing information through memory, thinking, reasoning and then giving a response based on knowledge and experience, which can occur during physical activities and/or games.

Physical Education and Aesthetic: In the process of physical perfection key position is taken by physical preparation of students, where dominating place is held by development of physical qualities: strength, quickness, dexterity, endurance, flexibility; all these qualities are reconditioning to aesthetic mastering of reality and to large extent characterize person's readiness for life, for practical activity in compliance with "the laws of beauty". On the other hand, high level of physical development creates precondition for easy and gracious movements that permits to speak, in general, about culture of movements as qualitative, aesthetic side of physical exercises.

Physical Education and Moral Values: Values education is very important for supporting and directing the attitudes and behaviours that brings from birth and changes by the effects of surroundings. The most effective people to provide this support after family are the teachers, especially the physical education teachers who are constantly communicating with the students. Therefore, teachers' perception and knowledge level for this concept should be determined. Physical education teachers teaching values through physical education contributes to personal development. According to Physical education teachers, the lesson gives students characteristics such as

acting together, motivating friends, fair play, helping friends, responsibility, feeling comfortable and free, respecting others' rights and equality. In addition, teachers consider their lesson more prioritizes Physical Education curriculum than the other curriculum subjects, and they advocate that values are taught within hidden curriculum, though not directly.

Benefits of Holistic Learning through Physical Education

Improved Academic Achievement: Holistic education can improve the academic achievements of all children, regardless of background and circumstances, by catering to individual learning styles and providing a supportive learning environment. Children's brain capacities are increased when they feel physically and emotionally safe and connected to others.

Enhanced Mental and Emotional Well-Being: In a supportive environment, where social and emotional learning is emphasized along with academics, students have a better chance of emerging with self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of social responsibility.

Increased Problem-Solving Ability: Students who are tasked with solving real-world problems that exist in their communities emerge with strong critical-thinking skills. These hands-on projects give students skills that will apply to their adult careers, such as how to gather, analyze, and report data and how to collaborate with others.

Reduced Impact of Inequities: By emphasizing integrated learning concepts, the whole-child approach to education has been shown to reduce the psychological impact of issues such as violence, abuse, or poverty on academic achievement, according to the Learning Policy Institute.

Conclusion

Holistic education is based on a learning philosophy that brings a number of benefits to students, teachers, schools, and communities. Students are empowered to improve their educational outcomes and gain the life skills necessary to take on a successful professional. In this method faces four main challenges to physical education were prevalent in the selected studies on holistic education: (1) the changing role of educators; (2) developing a standardised curriculum; (3) measurability issues in holistic education outcomes; and (4) the ability of students to adapt to holistic learning practices career. Adaptation can be described as the adjustment of the individual to his/her environment and the assimilation of experiences within a constant and active process. Practically, as individuals interact with their environment, they get accustomed to routines and gradually they build their understanding and learn how to adjust themselves and their actions accordingly. It also means that the skills can be used adequately in different situations. These are all the main benefits which we introducing Physical education modules in the curriculum are enhances the learning aptitude of the students, improves cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, flexibility, mobility, and body consumption, helps in improving power, agility, reaction, time, balance, speed, and coordination by use of all senses, develops interpersonal skills of the students like teamwork, leadership, communication, etc. Helps students combat mental health issues like stress and anxiety. It also helps build resilience and emotional stability. And also helps in still a sense of confidence and helps students attain a sense of individuality.

References

- [1] Bailey, R. (2018). Sport, physical education and educational worth. *Educ. Rev.*, 70, 51–66.
- [2] Hare, J. *Holistic Education: An Interpretation for Teachers in the IB Programmes*; International Baccalaureate Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2010; pp. 3–8. Available online: <https://balicurriculum.files.wordpress.com/2010/08/holistic-education-an-interpretation-for-teachers-in-the-ib-programmes.pdf> (accessed on 24 February 2022).
- [3] Naul, R.; Scheuer, C. (2020). *Research on Physical Education and School Sport in Europe*; Meyer & Meyer: Aachen, Germany, ISBN 3840313856.3.
- [4] Robinson, L.E.; Stodden, D.F.; Barnett, L.M.; Lopes, V.P.; Logan, S.W.; Rodrigues, L.P.; D'Hondt, E. (2015). Motor competence and its effect on positive developmental trajectories of health. *Sports Med.*, 45, 1273–1284.

COGNITIVE STUDY OF ENSEMBLE THE OPTIMAL SOFTWARE TESTING TECHNIQUES AND APPROACHES

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Abstract

Software testing can be stated as the process of verifying and validating whether a software or application is bug-free, meets the technical requirements as guided by its design, development, and meets the user requirements effectively and efficiently by handling all the exceptional and boundary cases. The process of software testing aims not only at finding faults in the existing software but also to find the measures to improve the software in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and usability. It mainly aims at measuring the specification, functionality, and performance of a software program. To test software completely, need to do its validation and verification before handling it to the customer. So, for this purpose, software techniques and software testing strategies are developed. Software testing techniques are the ways employed to test the application under test against the functional or non-functional requirements gathered from business. Each testing technique helps to find a specific type of defect. The main goal of software testing is to find bugs as early as possible and fix bugs and make sure that the software is bug-free. The goals of software testing may be classified into three major categories as follows: immediate goals, long term goals, post-implementation goals. This paper describes about software testing and its aspects like software testing techniques and software testing strategies.

Keywords: *Software Testing, Software Testing Strategies, Testing Techniques, Test Cases.*

Introduction

Software Testing is the process of identifying the accuracy and quality of the software product and service under test. Apparently, it was born to validate whether the product fulfills the particular prerequisites, needs, and desires of the client. At the end of the day, testing executes a framework or application with a specific end goal to point out bugs, errors or defects. The responsibility of testing is to point out the issues of bugs and give Dev (Developers) a clue to help them fix it right following the requirements. To all worries it provides cost effective solution. It provides enhanced product to customer in terms of functionality, accuracy, data security etc. It is an iterative process. It continues after the product is completed. The main objective of software testing is to verify Uncover as many as errors (or bugs) as possible in a given product. Validate the quality of a software using the minimum cost and efforts. Demonstrate a given software product matching its requirement specifications. Software testing is often divided into 2 main processes: Verification and Validation. Verification in software testing is the process when your team just need to check whether the software, system or framework consistent, aligned with the requirements of a documentation. Validation is the process that your team needs to verify the accuracy of the system. In this process, you will look back to the product, system and think about what users actually want and what has been done. In simple terms in order to make sure that the released software is safe and it's functioning as expected. The concept of software testing was introduced. It is important because software bugs, errors and defects can potentially leads to expenses and dangerous consequences. Software testing is exceptionally imaginative intellectual task for testers to perform. There are principles that every testers should aware of while performing software. Different issues are involved in software testing like scalability, usability, security.

Litreature Survey

In 2019, Authors Azeem Uddin and Abhineet Anand, from Galgotias University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India presented paper titled "Importance of Software Testing in the Process of Software Development". This paper is published in International Journal for Scientific Research Development| Vol. 6, Issue 12, 2019. Comparative study of present scenario of software testing with regard to testing in early days is done. Described about the objectives of software testing and also about different levels of software testing. Moreover, this paper focuses on Why to test. This paper presented a comprehensive account of all the terminologies that are related to software testing. [1]. In 2017, Author Himanshi Babbar presented paper titled " software testing: techniques and test cases ". this paper is published in international journal of research in computer applications and robotics, vol.5 issue 3, pg.: 44-53 march 2017. In this paper Whenever think of developing any software we always concentrate on making the software bug free and most reliable. At this point of time Testing is used to make the software a bug free. There are many test cases that help in detecting the bugs so, in this paper we describe about the most commonly used test cases and testing techniques for the error detection. [3]. In 2017, Authors Ms Ankita sethi

from IPEM Group of Institutions presented paper titled "A review paper on levels on levels, types and techniques in software testing". This paper is published in International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science, Volume 8, No. 7, July – August 2017. In this paper different types of testing are discussed. Different software testing techniques have mentioned. [3].

In 2016, Author Rajendra Kumar presented paper titled "Software testing technique and Strategies". This paper is published in International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology, 2016 Vol. 2, Issue 2. This paper on Software testing describes in detail about software testing, need of software testing, software testing goals and principles. Different Software testing techniques such as Correctness testing, Performance testing, Reliability testing, security testing. Discussed about grey box testing, about its strategies. [4]. In 2014, Author K. Rajasri, and T. Godwin Selva Raja from Christ College of engineering and technology, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, India, presented paper titled "An Evolution of Testing in Software Engineering" This paper is published in International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering Technology Volume 3, Issue 2. This paper addressed all major points of Software Testing Life Cycle (STLC) and the testing importance Bug Report. Detail information about bug reporting is explained. Bug reporting and importance and quality assurance for the applications is the main focus of the paper. [5]. In 2013, Author Shruti N. Pardeshi from Medicaps Institute of Science and Technology, Indore, India presented paper title "Study of Testing Strategies and available Tools". This paper is published in International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 3, March 2013. In this paper various different strategies of testing is described. Available testing tools and there necessity is described. [6].

Methodology

Software testing methodologies are the various strategies or approaches used to test an application to ensure it behaves and looks as expected. These encompass everything from front to back-end testing, including unit and system testing. There basics life cycles which is required while developing software are mentioned below.

Software Development Life Cycle

SDLC is a process followed for a software project, within a software organization. It consists of a detailed plan describing how to develop, maintain, replace and alter or enhance specific software. The life cycle defines a methodology for improving the quality of software and the overall development process. It works efficiently and effectively in the present information technology infrastructure available. Software Development Life Cycle is used to improve the development process. It shortens the time required for the production. It gives a structure to developers, which they can prefers while developing any product or application. Software Development Life Cycle provide basis to project. SDLC is important for developing a software system. It offers a basis for project planning, scheduling, and estimating. Provides a framework for a standard set of activities and deliverables. It is a mechanism for project tracking and control. Increases visibility of project planning to all involved stakeholders of the development process. Improved client relations. Helps you to decrease project risk and project management plan overhead Increased and enhance development speed .

Fig 1: Software Development Life cycle

Different phases of Software Development Life Cycle is shown in above fig 1.

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Each phase of Software Development Life Cycle is explained below.

Requirement gathering

Requirement gathering and analysis is the most important phase in the software development lifecycle. Requirement phase is the first step of the SDLC. Business Analyst collects the requirement from the Customer/Client as per the clients business needs and documents the requirements in the Business Requirement Specification (document name varies depends upon the Organization. Some examples are Customer Requirement Specification (CRS), Business Specification (BS). After gathering all the information, analysis can be done on product to decide how much time will require to develop a product, how much resources will require, what are limitations, what is the benefits of the product and also some other item will be considered. From these analysis we will get know that how much is the feasibility of the product. In this phase requirement document should get finalized so that developers and also customer can refer that document in further.

Analysis

Once the requirement gathering and analysis is done the next step is to define and document the product requirements and get them approved by the customer. This is done through the SRS (Software Requirement Specification) document. SRS consists of all the product requirements to be designed and developed during the project life cycle. Key people involved in this phase are Project Manager, Business Analyst and Senior members of the Team. The outcome of this phase is the Software Requirement Specification. In this phase of development all features, architecture of the product, all the necessary specifications proposed system which will require are designed. Software can be designed in two ways. Those ways are high level design and low level design. In high level design brief description of architecture is specified, what functionality will be require for designing module is outlined, interface specification are discussed, architecture information and its diagram is prepared, identification of database, details of technology along with architectural diagram. In low level design structure of input and output items, how error message should appear, how should be the interface of the product, type and size of the database, dependencies issues should be mentioned all these point are specified. This information will help developers to understand overall architecture of the system.

Design

Design has two steps: HLD – High-Level Design – It gives the architecture of the software product to be developed and is done by architects and senior developers. LLD – Low-Level Design – It is done by senior developers. It describes how each and every feature in the product should work and how every component should work. Here, only the design will be there and not the code. The outcome from this phase is High-Level Document and Low-Level Document which works as an input to the next phase. The design stage takes as its initial input the requirements identified in the approved requirements document.

Coding

In this phase of SDLC, the actual development begins, and the programming is built. The implementation of design begins concerning writing code. Developers have to follow the coding guidelines described by their management and programming tools like compilers, interpreters, debuggers, etc. are used to develop and implement the code. Coding starts once the developer gets the Design document. The Software design is translated into source code. All the components of the software are implemented in this phase.

Testing

The phase entails the evaluation of the created software. The testing team evaluates the developed product(s) in order to assess whether they meet the requirements specified in the 'planning' phase. Assessments entail the performance of functional testing: unit testing, code quality testing, integration testing, system testing, security testing, performance testing and acceptance testing, as well as nonfunctional testing. If a defect is identified, developers are notified. Validated (actual) defects are resolved, and a new version of the software is produced. During this stage, unit testing, integration testing, system testing, acceptance testing are done.

Deployment

Once the product is tested, it is deployed in the production environment or first UAT (User Acceptance testing) is done depending on the customer expectation. In the case of UAT, a replica of the production environment is created and the customer along with the developers does the testing. If the customer finds the

application as expected, then sign off is provided by the customer to go live. After the deployment of a product on the production environment, maintenance of the product i.e. if any issue comes up and needs to be fixed or any enhancement is to be done is taken care by the developers.

Software Testing Life Cycle

Software Testing Life Cycle consists different testing activities which should be conducted in the sequence while testing. The main aim of this life cycle is that it should meet quality goals. Software testing phase plays vital part in Software Development Life Cycle. Testing team needs to plan many activities. Every activity should be quality oriented. Every team needs to know its ultimate scope whenever they starts planning any follow. Similarly, at a very early stage testing should be able to analyse the scope of testing for the product. Each and every document prepared by testing team should be in a proper way and each step should be understandable. If all test scenarios are covered properly as per the requirement, then it will take less time to execute test suit. This will help to find bugs at early stage.

Fig 2: Software Testing Life Cycle

Different phases of testing life cycle are shown in Fig 2.

Each phase of Software Development Testing Life Cycle is explained below.

Requirement Analysis

Requirement Analysis is the first step of Software Testing Life Cycle (STLC). In this phase quality assurance team understands the requirements like what is to be tested. If anything is missing or not understandable then quality assurance team meets with the stakeholders to better understand the detail knowledge of requirement. Once testers and QA team understands requirement properly, it gives them clear idea about which type of testing will be required to test the product. Testing priorities can be set from this. Testers can set Environment for testing.

Test Planning

Test Planning is most efficient phase of software testing life cycle where all testing plans are defined. In this phase manager of the testing team calculates estimated effort and cost for the testing work. This phase gets started once the requirement gathering phase is completed. Testing team decides that which environment will require for testing and which types of testing will be done.

Test Case Development

The test case development phase gets started once the test planning phase is completed. In this phase testing team note down the detailed test cases. Testing team also prepare the required test data for the testing. When the test cases are prepared then they are reviewed by quality assurance team.

Test Environment Setup

Test environment setup is the vital part of the STLC. Basically test environment decides the conditions on which software is tested. This is independent activity and can be started along with test case development. In this process the testing team is not involved. The developer or the customer creates the testing Environment. Test environment is created by developer and customer.

Test Execution

After the test case development and test environment setup test execution phase gets started. In this phase testing team start executing test cases based on prepared test cases in the earlier step.. Testers retest that bug and mark it as close if it is fixed or reopens it if it not fixed.

Test Cycle Closure

Test Cycle Closure phase is completion of test execution which involves several activities like test completion reporting, collection of test completion matrices and test results. Testing team members meet, discuss and analyze testing artifacts to identify strategies that have to be implemented in future, taking lessons from current test cycle. The idea is to remove process bottlenecks for future test cycles. Evaluate cycle completion criteria based on Time, Test coverage, Cost, Software, Critical Business Objectives, Quality. Prepare test metrics based on the above parameters.

Bug Life Cycle

Bug life cycle goes through different phases. Bug life cycle starts when tester found new issue and ends when tester closes that issue. Bug life cycle differs from project to project.

Fig 3: Bug Life Cycle

Fig 3 shows different phases of Bug Life Cycle. New: When a defect is to find, logged and posted for the first time. Its state is given as new. Assigned: Once the bug is posted by the tester, the lead of the tester approves the bug and assigns the bug to the developer team. There can be two scenarios, first that the defect can directly assign to the developer, who owns the functionality of the defect. Open: Its state when the developer starts analyzing and working on the defect fix. Fixed: When developer makes necessary code changes and verifies the changes then he/she can make bug status as 'Fixed'. Retest: At this stage the tester do the retesting of the changed code which developer has given to him to check whether the defect got fixed or not. Once the latest build is pushed to the environment, Dev lead move all the Fixed defects to Retest. It is an indication to the testing team that the defects are ready to test. Reopened: If the bug still exists even after the bug is fixed by the developer, the tester changes the status to "reopened". The bug goes through the life cycle once again. Deferred: The bug, changed to deferred state means the bug is expected to be fixed in next releases. The reasons for changing the bug to this state have many factors. Rejected: If the developer feels that the bug is not genuine, developer rejects the bug. Then the state of the bug is changed to "rejected". Duplicate : If the bug is repeated twice or the two bugs mention the same concept of the bug, then the recent/latest bug status is changed to "duplicate". Closed: Once the bug is fixed, it is tested by the tester. If the tester feels that the bug no longer exists in the software, tester changes the status of the bug to "closed". This state means that the bug is fixed, tested and approved.

Software Testing Techniques

After the code is develop successfully, tester's needs to test the functionality of the system. Software testing techniques are broadly categorized into two parts. Those parts are static testing and dynamic testing.

Manual Testing (Static Testing)

Static Testing is a type of a Software Testing method which is performed to check the defects in software without actually executing the code of the software application. Whereas in Dynamic Testing checks the code is executed to detect the defects. Static testing is performed in early stage of development to avoid errors as it is easier to find sources of failures and it can be fixed easily. The errors that can't not be found using Dynamic Testing, can be easily found by Static Testing.

Steps of Manual Testing

Step 1: The Testing process begins with understanding the application to be tested and what the end-user should expect from the product. This is done by reviewing all available documents, studying any existing systems and integrations, and by interacting with stakeholders to understand their business requirements.

Step 2: Once the requirements are understood, and a basic framework of how to proceed is taking shape, the test environment can be prepared. By setting up well in advance, enough time can be factored in for obtaining and setting up manual testing tools, hardware, and other subsidiary materials and assets needed for the test runs

Step 3: Following the analysis of requirements and user stories, understanding what and how to test will have become clear. For projects that adhere to process, documentation is necessary, which usually includes writing test cases. When test planning starts and documents have been shared with the team, testers review the specification documents in detail, gather in-depth knowledge about the scope of testing, and then create high-level test scenarios and detailed level test cases.

Steps 4: The pivotal activity in software testing is test execution. In manual testing, each test case is performed by one or more people who take action based on the instructions laid out in the test cases. The tester's focus is to achieve the stated objective while noting any deviation between the expected and actual.

Step 5: Every failed test will be associated with a defect. The purpose of testing is not limited to identifying and reporting found defects, but also to ensure that all reported problems have been acknowledged, fixed, and then retested for confirmation. Once the developers have returned a fixed issue, it is the tester's responsibility to retest the reported defect to confirm the fix so the ticket can be legitimately marked as closed. Once it has been proved that the product functions successfully according to the requirements of the business owner, the item can be transferred to a release manager and scheduled for release

Automation Testing (Dynamic Testing)

Dynamic Testing is a type of Software Testing which is performed to analyze the dynamic behavior of the code. It includes the testing of the software for the input values and output values that are analyzed. Dynamic Testing is basically performed to describe the dynamic behavior of code. It refers to the observation of the physical response from the system to variables that are not constant and change with time. To perform dynamic testing the software should be compiled and run.

Step 8: Writing Scripts

Step 9: Reporting and Maintenance of scripts

Software Testing Strategies

Software testing strategies are very important in order to construct software successfully. Software testing strategies combines test cases design methods. Software Testing is a type of investigation to find out if there is any default or error present in the software so that the errors can be reduced or removed to increase the quality of the software and to check whether it fulfills the specifies requirements or not. Four types of testing strategies are there. Explanation of each strategy is given below.

Unit Testing

Unit testing involves the testing of each unit or an individual component of the software application. It is the first level of functional testing. The aim behind unit testing is to validate unit components with its performance. A unit is a single testable part of a software system and tested during the development phase of the application software .The purpose of unit testing is to test the correctness of isolated code. A unit component is an individual function or code of the application. White box testing approach used for unit testing and usually done by the developers.

Integration Testing

Integration testing is the second level of the software testing process comes after unit testing. In this testing, units or individual components of the software are tested in a group. The focus of the integration testing level is to expose defects at the time of interaction between integrated components or units. Unit testing uses modules for testing purpose, and these modules are combined and tested in integration testing. The Software is developed with a number of software modules that are coded by different coders or programmers. The goal of integration testing is to check the correctness of communication among all the modules.

Fig 4: Unit testing and Integration testing

System Testing

System Testing includes testing of a fully integrated software system. Generally, a computer system is made with the integration of software (any software is only a single element of a computer system). The software is developed in units and then interfaced with other software and hardware to create a complete computer system. In other words, a computer system consists of a group of software to perform the various tasks, but only software cannot perform the task; for that software must be interfaced with compatible hardware. System testing is a series of different type of tests with the purpose to exercise and examine the full working of an integrated software computer system against requirements.

Acceptance Testing

Acceptance testing is formal testing based on user requirements and function processing. It determines whether the software is conforming specified requirements and user requirements or not. It is conducted as a kind of Black Box testing where the number of required users involved testing the acceptance level of the system. It is the fourth and last level of software testing.

Results and Discussion

Testing can show the presence of faults in a system; it cannot prove there are no remaining bugs. Component developers are responsible for component testing; system testing is the responsibility of a separate team. Integration testing is testing increments of the system; release testing involves testing a system to be released to a customer. Use experience and guidelines to design test cases in defect testing. Interface testing is designed to discover defects in the interfaces of composite components. Software testing aims to make software stable. High quality product, can be produce by performing software testing. It focuses always on the expected result. Customer requirements must be high priority of testers. For performing a quality testing, tester should know testing strategies. Also method of reporting bugs is very important in software testing. Each and every scenario of software should get tested. By doing this practice, improvisation of software will happen at every stage. It is also very important to choose correct testing techniques. Tester should have the knowledge of what testing techniques should be used at different stages while building software.

Conclusion

Software testing strategies and software testing techniques are discussed in this paper. Moreover, it provides information on each phase of Software Development Life Cycle, Software Testing Life Cycle and Bug Life Cycle. These life cycles help in improving the quality of software and in overall development process of software. By using these standard testing techniques and testing strategies a stable and robust product can get delivered to end user. Testing is the most basic aspect of the Software Development Lifecycle, as it is something whereupon the last conveyance of the item is needy. It is tedious and a serious cycle, subsequently, improved procedures and inventive techniques are essential. This makes Automated Testing and different Test Metrics

execution previously and during the testing cycle. It can improve the current testing strategies, both for time adequacy just as for effective and dependable last item which meets the predefined prerequisites as well as furnishes with most extreme operations.

References

- [1] Pavithra L and Sandhya S "Survey on Software Testing". Journal of Network Communications and Emerging Technologies (JNCET) Volume 9, Issue 3 March 2019.
- [2] Arti Rana, Arvind Singh Rawat and Anchit Bijalwan "Process of finding defects in software testing" Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Research in Intelligent and Computing in Engineering, ACSIS ISSN 2300-5963, 2017.
- [3] Himanshi Babbar "SOFTWARE TESTING: TECHNIQUES AND TEST CASES" International journal of research in computer applications and robotics (ijrcar), ISSN 2320-7345, Vol.5 Issue 3, 2017.
- [4] Shalini Gautam, and Bharti Nagpal "Descriptive Study of Software Testing & Testing Tools" International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering (IJIRCCE) Vol. 4, Issue 6, June 2016.
- [5] Tanuj Wala and Aman Kumar Sharma "Improvised Software Testing Tool " International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing (IJCSMC) , Vol. 3, Issue. 9, September 2014.
- [6] Dr.A.Chandrasekar , Mrs.SudhaRajesh and Mr.P.Rajesh "A Research Study on Software Quality Attributes" International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 4, Issue 1, January 2014.
- [7] Maneela Tuteja and Gaurav Dubey "A Research Study on importance of Testing and Quality Assurance in Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) Models" International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE) Volume-2, Issue-3, July 2012.
- [8] Stacey, D. A., "Software Testing Techniques"
- [9] Guide to the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge, Swebok – A project of the IEEE Computer Society Professional

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

UTILIZATION OF E-LEARNING RESOURCES TO ENHANCE HOLISTIC EDUCATION AMONG THE PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

The current study looks at how potential instructors utilization of e-learning resources to improve their holistic education. The study's sample was chosen using the stratified sampling method, and it consisted of 360 people (180 boys and 180 girls) from the Sivagangai area. Stratified sampling was used to choose the sample. The usage of online learning resources and the investigator's ability to teach were tools for the research. The results also showed that male and female prospective teachers use e-learning resources in very different ways. When it comes to their group-teaching proficiency, aspiring teachers in the arts and sciences differ significantly. The study suggests that prospective teachers in B.Ed. colleges receive institutional-based training throughout their internship term on how to access and use e-learning resources. When they are using the e-learning resources and there prospective teacher's holistic education is how to improve. Finally the study reveals that the holistic education of prospective teachers while using of e-learning resources the science student teachers are very satisfied.

Keywords: *Utilization, E-Learning Resources, Holistic Education, Prospective Teachers*

Introduction

E-learning provides students with all kinds of educational needs and guidance for their future career education. The main contributor to that are e-learning resources. In general the learning resources are promoting the holistic education. Thus the interest, ability and functionality of the students prevail. Similarly learning resources are also an important aspect for the skill development of students. It is an undeniable fact that students are learning more and more educational techniques through e-learning than traditional method learning. The self learning process prevails. Especially today there are a lot of important resources like You-tube, Face book, Twitter, WhatsApp, Wikipedia, Google Classroom. When their using the e-learning resources, the prospective teachers how they are improve the knowledge and holistic values. The holistic education is a comprehensive approach to teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format.

E-Learning Resources

Most of the e-learning resources are using by the students and teachers. The investigator mainly used and utilization some e-learning resources and how to improved the prospective teacher's holistic education. There is You-Tube, Google class room, WhatsApp, Blogs, Face book etc. In this study all the e-learning resources to enhance holistic education for prospective teachers. Mainly the investigator used few resources in this study. Below is a description of the e-learning resources used by most pre-service teachers in the research conducted by the investigator.

Holistic Education

A teaching strategy known as holistic education places equal emphasis on students' social and academic demands. The goal of the educators is to satisfy the students' academic needs. And show them how to use the appropriate techniques to deal with life's obstacles. They make an effort to involve the learner on all levels, including the intellect, spirit, and body. The focus of this instructional strategy is on creating a supportive environment in schools. Additionally, the pupils' favourable social behaviours are a result of their cognitive talents.

Need for the Study

It is no exaggeration to say that in today's modern age e-learning has gained importance in all fields. Through this study the investigator highlights the level of holistic education of prospective teachers when using e-learning resources. A plenty of learning resources are available to help students complete their holistic activities effectively. This study aims to quantify the scope of educational activities, particularly those involving e-

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learning resources. Investigator examines how a prospective teacher uses e-learning resources during the internship training period and therefore the educational progress that students make. The essence of the study is to expose students learning directory by using e-learning resources to subject all grades of students to the school. To engage students in projects that applies critical-thinking skills toward solving real-world problems. Second year B.Ed. students were utilizing the e-learning resources to conduct lessons for students during their ITP period and to test the resulting learning outcomes. The need for this study illustrates that the change we bring to the student community will create a better society for tomorrow.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To measure the level of e-learning resources of prospective teachers.
- 2) To calculate the level of holistic education of prospective teachers.
- 3) To find out the significant difference in the level of e-learning resources among the prospective teachers on the basis of gender and subject of study.
- 4) To identify the significant difference in the level of holistic education among the prospective teachers on the basis of sub variables.
- 5) To find out the relationship between e-learning resources and holistic education of prospective teachers in terms of the demographic variables.

Tool Used for the Study

Utilization of e-learning resources and holistic education scale validated by the investigator with the help of the guide Dr. G. Sivakumar was used in this study.

Population of the Study

The samples selected for this research is B.Ed. colleges in Sivagangai district.

Analysis of E-learning Resources obtained by the prospective teachers

Hypothesis: 1

(H₀): There is no significant difference in the level of E-learning Resources obtained by the prospective teachers

Table: 1 Utilization of E-Learning Resources

Level	No. of sample	Percentage
High (24-40)	198	55%
Moderate(15-23)	130	36.11%
Low(0-14)	32	8.89%

Figure: 1 E-Learning Resource

Analysis of Holistic Education Level Among Prospective Teachers

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Hypothesis-2

(H₀): There is no significant difference in the level of holistic obtained by the prospective teachers.

TABLE 2

Level of Holistic Education	No .of Students	Percentage of Sample
High(34-50)	149	41.39%
Moderate(17-33)	183	50.83%
Low(0-16)	28	7.78%

Figure 2

Holistic Education

Hypothesis 3

(H₀)- There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of e-learning resources between male and female prospective teachers.

Table 3 Difference Between The Male And The Female Prospective Teachers In Their Utilization Of E-Learning Resources

Variable	Gender	Mean	S.D	N	't' Value	Significant Level
UELRL	Male	43.27	4.45	180	1.66	Not Significant
	Female	44.04	4.34	180		

HYPOTHESIS 4

(H₀)- There is no significant difference in the level of Holistic Education between male and female prospective teachers.

Table 4 Difference Between The Male And The Female Prospective Teachers In Their Holistic Education

Variable	Gender	Mean	S.D	N	't' Value	Significant level
HE	Male	35.51	5.26	180	3.92	significant
	Female	37.58	4.74	180		

From the table, it is evident that the calculated 't' value 3.93 is greater than the table 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

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Hypothesis -5

(H0)- There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of e-learning resources between arts and science prospective teachers.

Table 5 Difference Between The Arts And Science Prospective Teachers In Their Utilization Of E-Learning Resources

Variable	Type of course	Mean	S.D	N	't'Value	Significant level
UELR	Arts	43.52	4.36	210	0.62	Not significant
	Science	43.81	4.45	150		

The calculated t value 0.63 is lesser than the table t value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis -6

(H0)- There is no significant difference in the level of Holistic Education between arts and science prospective teachers.

Table 6 Difference Between Arts And Science Prospective Teachers In Their Utilization Of E-Learning Resources

Variable	Type of course	Mean	S.D	N	't'Value	Significant level
HE	Arts	37.56	5.12	210	3.89	Significant
	Science	35.48	4.83	150		

It is evident that the calculated 't' value 3.97 is greater than the table 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis-7

(H0)- There is no relationship between utilization of e-learning resources and Holistic Education among prospective teachers.

Table: 7 Relationship Between The Level Of Utilization Of E-Learning Resources And Holistic Education Of Prospective Teachers

Variables	Sample	No. of Sample	'r' Value	Level of Relationship
UELR	Prospective Teachers	360	0.342	Low + ve Relationship
HE				

From the above table is inferred that the calculated 'r' value 0.342 is greater than the table 'r' value 0.115 at 0.01 level of significance hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis-8

(H0) There is no relationship between e-learning resources and Holistic Education among the prospective teachers in terms of gender and type of course.

Table -8 Relationship Between The Level Of Utilization Of E-Learning Resources And Holistic

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Education Of Prospective Teachers Based On The Population Variables

Variables	Population variables	No. of Sample	'r' Value	Level of Relationship	
UELR & HE	Gender	Male	180	0.304	Low +ve relationship
		Female	180	0.38	Low +ve relationship
	Type of course	Arts	210	0.190	Negligible
		Science	150	0.750	High +ve relationship

Findings for Relationship Analysis

The level of utilization of e-learning resources has low positive relationship (0.304) at 0.01% level with the Holistic Education of prospective teacher's in male students. The level of utilization of e-learning resources has low positive relationship (0.38) at 0.01% level with the Holistic Education of prospective teacher's in female students. The level of utilization of e-learning resources has negligible (0.190) at 0.01% level with the Holistic Education of prospective teacher's in arts students. The level of utilization of e-learning resources has high positive relationship (0.750) at 0.01% level with the Holistic Education of prospective teacher's in science students.

Interpretation

The level of utilizing e-learning resources and Holistic Education of prospective teachers are comparatively high for female prospective teachers than the male prospective teachers. This may be due to in the fact that naturally females are the ones who can responsibly and efficiently in any job. Generally women are more capable than men in teaching using e-learning resources. The level of utilizing the e-learning resources of prospective teachers is comparatively high for science than the arts students. This might be because science students use online learning materials more frequently than arts students do for their academic needs. Used extensively for assignments, projects and experiments. The level of holistic education of prospective teachers is comparatively high for arts students than the science students. This may be due to the fact that the exhibit skills and talents in extra-curricular activities. They are involving all the general things especially sports, teaching skills, dance, mimicry etc. Therefore, students' learning ability will be natural to them as they have easy access to everyone. Also teaching ability will be better than science students.

Conclusion

Significantly, e-learning resources played a major role in the pandemic situation. And also it could not be superfluous if children to adults were able to meet their developmental needs through e-learning resources. When a few demographic variables were tested, neither the utilization of e-learning resources by men nor women changed. The way that science students and students of both arts and sciences use online learning tools is evolving. E-learning resources received a lot of support from both students and teachers during the recent COVID 19 Pandemic session.

References

- [1] Aggarwal, J.C , Essentials of educational technology: Teaching and learning, New Delhi: Vikas publishing house Pvt. Ltd.1995
- [2] Ajegbomogun, Fredrick Olatunji; Okunlaya, Rifqah Olufunmilayo Afolake; Alawiye, Mariam Kehinde, Analytical Study of E-Learning Resources in National Open University of Nigeria Education and Information Technologies, v22 n5 p2403-2415 sep 2017
- [3] Dufty, D, Dufty, H. (1994). Australian Curriculum Studies Association & Holistic Education Network, Holistic education: Some Australian explorations, Australian Curriculum Studies Association, Belconnen, A.C.T
- [4] Ismail, Sadiq Abdulwahed Ahmed; Jarrah, Adeb Mohamed, Exploring Pre-Service Teachers'

- Perceptions of Their Pedagogical Preferences, Teaching Competence and Motivation International Journal of Instruction, v12 n1 p493-510 Jan 2019
- [5] Jimenez, E. C., Contextualized E-Learning Resource: A Tool for Stronger Academic Platform Online Submission, International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE) v4 n2 p110-116 sep 2020
- [6] John W. Best & James. V. Kahn, "Research in Education", Prentice Hall of India (P) Ltd, New Delhi 1999
- [7] KellyB.PhippsL.SwiftE.Developing a holistic approach for e-learning accessibilityCanadian Journal of Learning and Technology
- [8] Olaniran, Sunday O.; Duma, M. A. N.; Nzima, D. R., Assessing the Utilization Level of E-Learning Resources among ODL Based Pre-Service Teacher Trainees Electronic Journal of e-Learning, v15 n5 p384-394 2017
- [9] Prieto-Ballester, Jorge-Mamuel; Revuelta-Dominguez, Francisco-Ignacio; Pedrera-Rodreguez, Maria-Inmaculada, Secondary School Teachers Self-Perception of Digital Teaching Competence in Spain Following COVID-19 Confinement Education Sciences, v11 Article 407 2021
- [10] Ramirez, Iris April L, Secondary Pre-Service Science Teachers' Competence: Theory to Practice International Online Journal of Education and Teaching, v8 n2 p662-675 2021
- [11] Ruzegea, Mboni; Msonde, Sydney University Students' E-Resource Usage: Predictors, Problems and Practical Implications International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology, v17 n2 p104-119 2021
- [12] Song, Huan; Zhou, Mingming, STEM Teachers' Preparation, Teaching Beliefs, and Perceived Teaching Competence: A Multi group Structural Equation Approach Journal of Science Education and Technology, v30 n3 p394-407 Jun 2021
- [13] Taffs, Kathryn H.; Holt, Julienne I. Investigating Student Use and Value of E-Learning Resources to Develop Academic Writing within the Discipline of Environmental Science Journal of Geography in Higher Education, v37 n4 p500-514 2013

STRATEGIES FOR DYSLEXIC CHILDREN IN INCLUSIVE CLASSROOM

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Abstract

Inclusive education refers to the inclusion of all children in the education system, regardless of their differences and disabilities. Inclusive education welcomes and celebrates diversity. Children with special educational needs require their learning to be tailored to meet desired learning objectives. In addition, children who have significantly greater difficulty learning often struggle to keep up with others of the same age, due to the severity of their disability, and therefore extra school support is needed. One of the most prevalent learning disabilities found among pupils is dyslexia, a disorder that impedes the development of literacy skills such as reading, writing, and spelling. Since this disorder affects learning and consequently performance it's necessary for schools to implement inclusive practice within the classroom to prevent the use of segregated schooling and ensure dyslexic pupils meet their educational goals. This paper discusses a number of promising teaching strategies utilized to help pupils with dyslexia such as technology, phonics, and scaffolding learning by appropriately altering their zone of proximal development.

Keywords: Inclusive education, dyslexic children, disability, Assistive technology

Introduction

Inclusive Education was also defined as a learning environment that promotes the full personal, academic and professional development of all learners irrespective of race, class, gender, disability, religion, culture, sexual preference, learning styles, and language (UNESCO, 1994). Randiki (2003) states that Inclusive Education is the process of addressing learners' needs within the mainstream of education using all available resources thus creating opportunities for learners in preparing them for life. The emphasis is on equality, access, retention and opportunity to educate by reviewing schools and systems changing them rather than trying to change the learners.

Dyslexia

Dyslexia can be described as a continuum of difficulties in learning to read, write and/or spell, which persist despite the provision of appropriate learning opportunities. These difficulties often do not reflect an individual's cognitive abilities and may not be typical of performance in other areas. The impact of dyslexia as a barrier to learning varies in degree according to the learning and teaching environment, as there are often associated difficulties such as:

- 1) auditory and/or visual processing of language-based information
 - 2) phonological awareness
 - 3) oral language skills and reading fluency
 - 4) short-term and working memory
 - 5) sequencing and directionality
 - 6) number skills
 - 7) organizational ability
- Developing inclusive and supportive learning environments.

Inclusive Classrooms And Student Learning

All students have varying social, economic, emotional, and academic experiences that impact the way they learn. An inclusive classroom sets every student up for success, whether they have a learning disability or other experiences that impact their learning style. Designing an inclusive classroom eliminates the need for special education classrooms and provides an environment where all students learn together. Inclusive classrooms help students combat the isolation that can come from being separated into a special education group while still providing the necessary accommodations that the students need to succeed. In an inclusive classroom, students with a disability, learning or otherwise, participate in the same lessons and activities as other students in their class. However, class activities are modified to be more accessible to the needs of students with a disability. Implementing differentiated instruction can boost the confidence of a student with dyslexia and ensure they feel

equal to their peers.

Visual Aids

Many students, including visual learners and students with dyslexia, benefit from increased visual aids in a classroom. Visual aids show a graphic or pictorial representation of the material being taught. Some ways that teachers can include visual examples in their classroom include:

- 1) Breaking up presentations, lectures, and blocks of text with pictures and diagrams.
- 2) Writing down key points on the board during class.
- 3) Using colorful posters and letter strips in the classroom to help with dyslexia spelling strategies.
- 4) Making mind maps to reinforce the content of a lesson.
- 5) Having students visualize the main points of a lesson.
- 6) Colour coding all materials.

Assistive Technology

Assistive technology can provide phonological dyslexia strategies that help students with dyslexia succeed in the classroom. Because technology is prevalent in today's society, incorporating assistive technologies in classroom settings is easy. One way is to incorporate assistive technology with other reading strategies for dyslexia. Technology such as audiobooks, videos, and text-to-speech software are excellent resources that help students with dyslexia master reading skills.

Extra Practice and Time

Teachers can include additional time in assignments by: Separating longer assignments, such as projects and essays, into smaller pieces with easily achievable goals. Providing extra lessons on reading and writing activities for students who need or want an additional review. Giving extra practice as independent work, tutoring, or extra credit. Individual Education Plans (IEP) are highly recommended for students with dyslexia, and teachers can develop them with the help of the student and their parent's input. By creating an IEP, teachers can establish the amount of extra time and practice that the student needs for assignments. Having an IEP will also ensure that the student is getting every opportunity to complete work and grasp lessons successfully.

Group Projects

Group projects are a great way to encourage the development of healthy socialization skills. In group projects, two or more students work together and use their strengths to complete an assignment. One advantage of collaborating in a group is that each student can take on a different role. Depending on the requirements of each role, some students in the group may not be doing an equal amount of reading or writing. Teachers can outline different roles for students in a group so that a student with dyslexia can participate without being required to complete tasks they struggle with. In addition to healthy socialization, group projects teach students to work together and combine the strengths of multiple people.

Appropriate Sensory Environment

It's estimated that 3 in 10 children with dyslexia also have ADHD. Students with dyslexia often require structure and organization in order to succeed in a classroom setting, and that need is heightened when paired with ADHD. Creating a sensory-friendly classroom helps students with sensory sensitivities, such as students with ADHD, by limiting distractions and helping students focus on the lesson. There are a few simple changes teachers can make to ensure their classroom is sensory-friendly:

- 1) Put tennis balls on the bottom of the chairs.
- 2) Use muted colors.
- 3) Have fidget toys available for students to use.
- 4) Keep the classroom organized.
- 5) Establish and post a classroom routine.
- 6) Provide a quiet space in the corner of a classroom for students to read or complete other assignments.

Have Patience and Good Communication

The best way to help a student with dyslexia is to create an open line of communication with the student and their parents about teaching and assessment strategies for students with dyslexia. Finding a learning plan that

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works for the student may take some trial and error; however, having open communication with the student and treating them with kindness and patience will help put the student on a path to success and limit feelings of failure or isolation. Maintaining open communication requires scheduling regular meetings with students and parents to evaluate the student's progress and assess areas of strength and weakness. Developing a set of strategies that best supports a student with dyslexia may take a lot of patience and communication, but watching them succeed will be worth it.

Support and Encourage

Students with dyslexia may get discouraged in school as they watch their peers easily grasp concepts that they struggle to understand. These challenges may cause students to lose motivation and believe that they are bad at school. However, students with dyslexia can still succeed with extra support and encouragement. Teachers play a pivotal role in the mental well-being and academic success of students with dyslexia by providing positive reinforcement, encouragement, and support students need. Teachers can watch students with dyslexia achieve academic and emotional success.

Encourage Self-Teaching

Many students advance their reading skills through self-teaching. Once students understand letters and basic phonetics, they can use those skills to puzzle out and eventually understand words they might not have encountered before. Help the child memorize sight words.

- 1) Provide reading material with simple, single vowel words.
- 2) Offer reading materials from a variety of levels so each student can find one that challenges them without discouraging them.
- 3) Give frequent breaks.
- 4) Encourage students to re-read their favorite stories.

Self-teaching using these dyslexia decoding strategies can help students with dyslexia improve their reading skills and help them gain confidence by setting them up for success.

Conclusion

Around the world, children are excluded from schools where they belong because of disability, race, language, religion, gender, and poverty. But every child has the right to be supported by their parents and community to grow, learn, and develop in the early years, and, upon reaching school age, to go to school and be welcomed and included by teachers and peers alike. When all children, regardless of their differences, are educated together, everyone benefits—this is the cornerstone of inclusive education.

References

- [1] Ackerman, P. T., & Dykman, R. A. (1993). Phonological processes, confrontational naming, and immediate memory in dyslexia. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 26(9), 597-609.
- [2] Adi-Japha, E., Landau, Y. E., Frenkel, L., Teicher, M., Gross-Tsur, V., & Shalev, R. S. (2007). ADHD and dysgraphia: underlying mechanisms. *Cortex*, 43(6), 700-709.
- [3] Ahissar, M., Protopapas, A., Reid, M., & Merzenich, M. M. (2000). Auditory processing parallels reading abilities in adults. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 97(12), 6832-6837.
- [4] Allington, R. L. (1983). Fluency: The neglected reading goal. *The reading teacher*, 36(6), 556-561.
- [5] Alloway, T. P., Gathercole, S. E., Kirkwood, H., & Elliott, J. (2009). The cognitive and behavioral characteristics of children with low working memory. *Child development*, 80(2), 606-621.
- [6] American Psychological Association. (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual, 4th edn, Text Revision (DSM-IV-TR)*. American Psychiatric Association, Washington.
- [7] Anne J., E.Schwartz & D.McGhie-Richmond. (2009). *Preparing teachers for inclusive classrooms*. University of Toronto: teacher and teacher education journal homepage.
- [8] AniyamuzaalaJ.Rwampigi, (2013), *Including the Excluded: Addressing the Diverse Educational Needs for Learners with Special AbilitieS*

EFFECT OF SUPER CIRCUIT RESISTANCE TRAINING AND YOGIC PRACTICES ON SELECTED VARIABLE PHYSIOLOGICAL OF TRIBAL COLLEGE WOMEN KABADDI PLAYERS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of super circuit resistance training and yogic practices on selected physiological variable such as Muscular Strength of tribal college women kabaddi players. For this study, sixty (N=60) tribal college women kabaddi players from Bhadradi Kothagudem, Telangana state, India were selected randomly as subjects. The age of the subjects were ranged between 19 to 25 years. They were divided at random into four groups of fifteen each (n=15). Group-I underwent Super Circuit Resistance Training, Group-II underwent Yogic practices, Group-III underwent Combined Super circuit Resistance Training and Yogic Practices and Group-IV was acted as the Control group. The training period was limited to three days per week for twelve weeks. The dependent variables only selected for this study were Muscular Strength. All the subjects were tested prior to and immediately after the experimental period on the selected dependent variables. To analyse the data, ANCOVA and Scheffé's post hoc test was used. The level of the confidence was fixed at 0.05. The results of the study show that there was significant improvement in the selected physiological variable among tribal college women kabaddi players due to the influence of super circuit resistance training and yogic practices.

Keywords: *Super Circuit Resistance Training and Yogic Practices, Muscular Strength.*

Introduction

Kabaddi

The sports has a long history dating back to pre-historic times. It was probably invented to ward off croup attacks by individuals and vice-versa. The game was very popular in the southern part of Asia played in its different forms under different names. A dramatized version of the great Indian epic, the Mahabharata. The game, known as Hu-Tu-Tu in Western India, Ha-Do-Do in Eastern India & Bangladesh, Chedugudu in Southern India and Kaunbada in Northern India, has undergone a sea change through the ages. Modern Kabaddi is a synthesis of the game played in its various forms under different names.

Super Circuit Resistance Training

Super circuit resistance training weight training refers to a program in which running or other aerobic exercises are performed between sets. This training produces aerobic as well as strength benefits. Circuit training is a weight training system where you do exercises quickly one after another for aerobic benefits as well as strength gains. Super Circuit training combined the weight lifting exercises of circuit training with interval cardio training.

Yoga

The term Yoga has been derived from the word unity. The Indus Valley civilization in South Asia is an old system of both physical and mental exercise. In Yoga sutra of Patanjali, 200BC, the earliest written records of these methodologies emerged. The system was an 8 track or Asthanga Yoga. Yoga has been described in many ways in modern literature.

Muscular Strength

Muscular Strength is a condition ability which depends largely on the energy liberation in the muscular strength is also perhaps the ability in sports, Muscular Strength is the ability to overcome the resistance or act against resistance. The ability to apply force and overcome resistance strength is an essential element in physical performance.

Methodology

Selection of the Subjects

To achieve the purpose of this study, sixty subjects were randomly selected from Bhadradi Kothagudem, Telangana State, India. The age of the subjects were ranged between 19 to 25 years. They were divided at random into four group of fifteen each (n=15). Group I underwent to super circuit resistance training, Group II underwent to Yogic Practices, Group III Underwent to Combined Super Circuit Resistance Training and Yogic Practices and Group –IV acted as the Control group. All the subjects were fully informed regarding nature of the experimental methodology and the subjects gave their consent to participate in this investigation.

Selection of the Variables

Independent Variables

- 1) Super circuit resistance training
- 2) Yogic Practices
- 3) Combined super circuit resistance training and Yogic Practices

Dependent Variable

Muscular Strength

Experimental Design

The study was formulated as a true random group design, Consisting of a Pre Test and Post Test. The subjects (N=60) were randomly assigned to four equal groups. The groups were assigned as Experimental group I Super circuit resistance training, Group –II Yogic Practices, Group-III Combined Super circuit resistance training and Yogic practices and Group – IV Control group respectively. Pre – Test was conducted for all the subjects on selected physiological variables such as Muscular Strength. The experimental group participated in their respective Super circuit resistance training and Yogic practices for a period of twelve weeks. The Post –Test was conducted on the above said dependent variable after a period of twelve weeks in the respective treatments.

Statistical Technique

The data collected from the subjects were treated. Statistical analysis of Co-variance was used to find out the adjusted mean difference among the treatment groups. The Scheffe's post hoc test used to find out the paired mean significances.

Result on Muscular Strength

Table-1: The summary of Mean and dependent 't' Test for the Pre and Post Tests on of Muscular Strength Experimental group and control group

Mean	Super circuit resistance training	Yogic Practices group	Combined Super circuit resistance Training and Yogic practices group	Control group
Pre –Test	14.47	14.27	13.8	14.80
Post - Test	18.47	17.33	19.20	14.87
't' Test	3.86	2.82	5.62	0.05

*Significant at .05 level.

(Table value required for significance at. 0.05 level for 't'-test with df14 is 2.15).

Table- 1 Show that the Pre-Test and Post – Test mean of Muscular Strength for Super circuit Resistance Training, Yogic Practices group, Combined Super circuit Resistance Training and Yogic Practices group and control group are values of 14.47,14.27,13.8,14.80 Post Test:18.47,17.33,19.20 and 14.87,'t' Test:3.86,2.82,5.62 and 0.05 respectively. The table value required for significant difference with df 14 at 0.05 level is 2.15. It was conducted that experimental groups such as Super Circuit Resistance training group, Yogic Practices group, and Combined super circuit resistance training and Yogic Practices.

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Figure:1 The Pre-Test and Post Mean value Super circuit resistance training group Yogic practices group, Combined Super circuit resistance training Yogic practices group and control group.

Table –II Analysis of Covariance on Muscular Strength of Experimental Groups and Control Group

Test	Super circuit resistance training	Yogic Practices	Combined Super Circuit resistance training and yogic practices	Control group	Source of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F ratio
Pre-Test Mean	14.47	14.27	13.80	14.80	Between	7.87	3	2.62	0.59
					Within	247.47	56	4.42	
Post-Test Mean	18.47	17.33	19.20	14.87	Between	161.73	3	53.91	16.13
					Within	187.20	56	3.34	
Adjusted Post Test Mean	18.38	17.38	19.56	14.55	Between	201.02	3	67.01	50.01
					Within	73.69	55	1.34	

*Significance at 0.05 level of confidence
(Muscular Strength Score in Numbers)

Table value for df (3,56) at 0.05level=2.76 Table value for df (3,55) at 0.05 level = 2.78

Table –II The ‘F’ Ratio on the Muscular Strength variable is displayed in Table II. The calculated ‘F’ Ratio came out at 50.01. Since the obtained F ratio Adjusted post test scores was higher than the table value of 2.78 for degree of freedom 3 and 55 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence Muscular Strength. The result of the study indicate that there are significant differences among the adjusted post test means of super circuit resistance training group, Yogic Practices group, Combined super circuit resistance training group, Yogic Practices and control group in Muscular strength.

Figure:2 The Adjusted Post test Mean value Super circuit resistance training group, Yogic practices group, Combined super circuit resistance training and yogic practices and control group on Muscular Strength.

Discussion on Finding

Generally the results indicated significant Increases in efficiency of the selected variable during twelve weeks of Super circuit resistance training and Yogic practices. Hence the hypothesis was accepted at 0.05 level of confidence. Muscular Strength increases through super circuit resistance training and Yogic practices for experimental group when paired with control group.

Conclusion

It was concluded that there was significant improvement I selected variable physiological variable of Muscular Strength due to Super circuit resistance training an Yogic practices among Tribal college Women kabaddi players. The result of the study reveals that Super circuit resistance training an Yogic practices Would improve tribal college women kabaddi players physiological variable significantly.

References

- [1] Vinolia and Annadurai(2021) Effect of yogic practices on functional variable of spouse.
- [2] Ramos et at.,(2021): Effect of resistance circuit –based training on strength, Cardio respiratory fitness and body composition.
- [3] Wase and Getachew(2020): Effect of circuit training on selected health related physical fitness of 2nd – year sport science students at Ambo University, Ethiopia
- [4] Vinnedkumar (20222): Effect of Circuit training programme on Muscular Strength.

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META-ANALYSIS ON SELF-REGULATED LEARNING (SRL) IN INDIAN CONTEXT

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Abstract

Researchers use a systematic review to examine existing empirical studies on self-regulated learning (SRL). Recent methodological strides have made it possible for educational research to delve into how students learn. Self-regulated learning is an active approach in which students oversee, manage and control their attitudes, behavior and enthusiasm to increase the efficiency of their learning. The goal of the current study was to provide researchers with greater insight into self-regulated learning, as it is a pertinent learning approach in the current digital age. Through purposive sampling, 20 research studies conducted in India, which focused on self-regulated learning and its different components, were selected. Cognitive, metacognitive, motivation, self-efficacy are noticeably related components of SRL in the literature. This paper intends to show up the researches related to SRL in India. To gain a better understanding of SRL research in India, this paper aims to present a review of the current researches. In conclusion, future research directions on self-regulated learning in the technological age are discussed.

Keywords: *Self-Regulated Learning, Cognition, Metacognition, Motivation*

Introduction

Self-regulated learning is an inwardly-focused practice that involves organizing and adjusting one's thinking, feelings, and activities for the purpose of reaching personal goals (Zimmerman, 2003). According to Bandura (1986), this type of learning comprises of three psychological components: self-observation, self-judgement, and self-correction. It involves more than mere knowledge of an expertise and it requires one to be cognitively aware, self-motivated and to possess the aptitude to properly put into action the knowledge they have. With the progression of higher education, bringing with it new methods to help students to become self-regulated learners. A self-regulated learner is an individual who is actively engaged in their learning process in terms of meta-cognition, motivation and behavior. When a learner is conscious of and has control over their learning environment, it is known as Self-Regulated Learning (Kumar & Singh, 2019).

Rationale for the Study

India is a rapidly growing nation and has the second largest higher education system in the world. We are in a period where information is mostly accessible for free of cost through the internet and can be accessed by anyone, in any place and at any time. Yet it is up to the learner to decide how much knowledge they can acquire and how successful they can become, and this is determined by their level of interest, attitude and self-regulating skills. Numerous studies have investigated the noteworthy functions of SRL in education, which demonstrate that self-regulated learning techniques are a key indicator of academic achievement. Thus, this review study was carried out to get a clearer comprehension of the Indian researchers' insights of SRL and to identify potential research areas that could be explored in the future.

Research Questions

RQ1. How did the research papers reviewed differ in terms of demographics?

RQ2. What insights have Indian researchers provided about SRL?

Meta-Analysis On Srl

RQ1. How did the papers reviewed differ in terms of demographics?

An online search was conducted via Google Scholar to find 20 systematic research works focused on self-regulated learning, with various aspects, variables and dimensions, that were conducted in India between 2017 and 2022, using the key word "self-regulated learning" through the purposive sampling technique.

Table 1. Shows the demographic profile of the present study.

S. No.	Locale	Research Studies Reviewed
1	Punjab	4
2	Tamil Nadu	3
3	Chandigarh	2
4	New Delhi	2
5	Karnataka	2
6	Uttar Pradesh	1
7	Haryana	1
8	Patna	1
9	Rajasthan	1
10	Kolkata	1
11	Ranchi	1
12	Mumbai	1
Total		20

RQ2. What insights have Indian researchers provided about SRL?

Developing metacognition is an essential component in making students become self-regulated in their learning, and there are three parsimonious factors that are established to make up metacognition: planning, monitoring, and self-evaluation (Chakraborty & Chechi, 2019). Students who employ better meta-cognitive techniques have a higher level of interest and perceive more autonomy, as well as becoming more self-motivated to create a strategy of contemplation in SRL (Saxena, 2020). Self-regulation strategies that include cognitive, metacognitive, and motivational strategies are suitable for learners of all abilities, and these SRL strategies can enhance instruction as they help teachers to engage students in the learning process more actively (Deep, 2021). Students who use self-regulated strategies are inherently self-motivated and demonstrate to be independent learners, using both cognitive and meta-cognitive strategies (Mohan & Verma, 2020). There is a noticeable link between academic success and parental support, which has been found to have a constructive influence on SRL (Ghazee & Islam, 2021). There is a significant and positive association between SRL and parental participation (Keziah & Chamundeswari, 2019). Self-regulation is contingent on things like motivation, management of time, monitoring and control (Gupta & Mehtani, 2017). Highly motivated individuals are more likely to incorporate learning strategies correctly to manage their learning (Chechi et al., 2018).

Moreover, a study performed on undergraduate students by Kumar & Bhalla (2019) determined that study habits are more influential than effort and capability in terms of SRL. Having a good set of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) skills is essential for arranging the learning process, inculcating self-discipline, establishing proper study habits, and ultimately making a student's life more successful (Kumar & Singh, 2019). Better SRL skills will result in improved academic performance and intellectual capability (Kaushik & Jena, 2021). Furthermore, they can also positively influence the teaching-learning process by utilizing pedagogies and providing learners with the latest information from the educational realm (Mahendiran & Kumar, 2017). The affective learning experiences of students will shape their attitude towards becoming self-regulated learners (Thomas, 2022). Nevertheless, setting goals and making task strategies are common issues for students when engaging in self-regulated online learning (Sharma & Chintalapati, 2022). Additionally, active procrastination is substantially correlated with goal-setting and planning, seeking information, and remembering SRL strategies (Sundaramoorthy, 2018). Sundaramoorthy, J. (2019) conducted a study focusing on pre-service teachers which concluded that procrastination has a vital link to the organizing and adaptation of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies. The researcher created the Self-Regulated Strategy Development (SRSD) model which consists of 30 interventions that aid students with learning disabilities and other learners who face difficulty in learning (Sandhu & Zarabi, 2018). The interventions in self-regulation strategies on learning had a noteworthy impact on all aspects of self-efficacy, including self-confidence, efficacy expectations, attitude, and outcome expectation for students with learning difficulties (Zarabi, 2019). It was also observed that students who practiced yoga had a higher level of SRL (Srilakshmidevi, & Suseela, 2019).

Conclusion

When the literature review was conducted, it revealed that the following elements were considered to depict Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) in the most precise way: cognition, metacognition, motivation, academic success, wellbeing, self-evaluation, goal-setting, time-management and self-belief. Multiple studies have affirmed

that explicit teaching of SRL has beneficial effects within the classroom. Therefore, it is vital to investigate the role of teachers in facilitating SRL. To advance self-regulated learning, motivational programs should be merged with instructional strategies. Procrastination is a common impediment of the academic achievement and wellbeing of students (Chu & Choi, 2005). So that it is found from this review paper, active procrastination is positively correlated with SRL strategies. To increase a student's success in online learning, Cho and Heron (2015) suggest that goal setting, planning, and monitoring should be done in a self-regulated manner. To promote a culture of online learning and foster a positive attitude towards technology, students in higher education in India should incorporate self-regulated learning strategies into their studies. Students should apply self-regulated learning strategies in combination with technology. Self-regulated learning practices are essential not only for students, teachers, and teacher educators, but also for anyone who aims to be successful in their profession and attain their desired professional position.

References

- [1] Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1986.
- [2] Chakraborty, R., & Chechi, V. K. (2019). Validation of the Parsimonious Factor Structure of Metacognitive Component of Self Regulated Learning in the Indian Context. In MHRD sponsored National Seminar, Rethinking Education: Developing a Culture of Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India, from 12th–13th August.
- [3] Chechi, Vijay & Gupta, Jyoti. (2018). Self-Regulated Learning Strategies of First Year Undergraduate Students of Commerce. 12. 449-464.
- [4] Cho, M. H., & Heron, M. L. (2015). Self-regulated learning: the role of motivation, emotion, and use of learning strategies in students' learning experiences in a self-paced online mathematics course. *Distance Education*, 36(1), 80–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587919.2015.1019963>
- [5] Chu, A.H.C., & Choi, J.N. (2005). Rethinking procrastination: Positive effects of “active” procrastination behaviour on attitudes and performance. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 145,245–264. DOI: 10.3200/SOCP.145.3.245-264.
- [6] Deep, A. (2021). Patterns of strategy use and self-regulation conduct after self-regulated learning strategy instruction program (SRLSIP): A Qualitative Study.
- [7] Ghazee, B., & Islam, S (2021). A study of academic achievement in relation to parental encouragement and self-regulated learning skills among senior secondary school students 5. 16. 2277-7881.
- [8] Gupta, M., & Mehtani, D. (2017). Type of school, locality and gender as determinants of selfregulated learning among students: An empirical study. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences (IJRESS)*, 7(1).
- [9] Kaushik, P., & Jena, S. P. K. (2021). Self-Regulation learning strategies and academic performance in students with learning difficulty. *International Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 14(4), 172-177.

INFLUENCE OF RESILIENCE ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF B. ED TEACHER TRAINEES

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Abstract

This study has been undertaken with a view to find out the influence of resilience on emotional intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees survey method was adopted for this study. The investigator selected a sample of 100 B.Ed. teacher trainees from Colleges of Education in and around Karaikudi. To measure the influence of resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees, a self-constructed tool "Resilience and Emotional Intelligence assessment tool" was used. The results reveal that there is a significant difference between sub groups of the sample based on the variables such as gender and major subjects.

Keywords: Resilience, Emotional Intelligence And B.Ed. Teacher Trainees.

Introduction

Resilience is the ability to cope with mental and emotional crises and return to normal. This could be due to lack of emotional maturity or stability, hormonal issues, etc. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand, use, and manage one's own emotions in a positive way for stress relief, problem solving, and effective communication. If resilience and emotions are developed among the B.Ed. teacher trainees, they can handle situations and deal with upcoming problems. While the study aimed to influence of psychological resilience on emotional intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Review of Related Literature

Galli, & Gonzalez (2015). "Psychological resilience in sport: A review of the literature and implications for research and practice". The ability to respond positively to setbacks, obstacles, and failures is essential for any successful athlete. Although resilience has been studied in general psychology for several decades, it is only recently that researchers and practitioners have begun to explore the construct within the sport context. The purpose of this article is to review the current state of resilience scholarship in sport, and to offer guidelines for future research and interventions in this area. Studies of resilience in sport to date have either used experimental designs to investigate resilience to performance failure, or qualitative interview designs to understand the thoughts and beliefs of athletes who have successfully overcome adversity. Researchers who wish to study sport resilience in the future should think carefully about how they operationalise the construct. Furthermore, knowledge will be enhanced by the development of a sport-specific resilience measure and the use of more sophisticated qualitative approaches and advanced statistical modelling procedures. Sport practitioners can learn from resilience-building programmes developed in other settings as they, craft evidence-based interventions to enhance resilience in athletes. Gayathri, & Meenakshi (2013). "A literature review of emotional intelligence". This paper traces the evolution of emotional intelligence as a theory and goes on to give a literature review of the same. It discusses the different concepts and beliefs pertaining to emotion and cognition and how it culminated in the theory of emotional intelligence. It also discusses the three major models of emotional intelligence, their contribution to the theory and finally closes with a brief discussion on future improvement of the theory.

Need for the Study

As the investigator is a Teacher Educator in the Higher Education System, as per her observation the students are found to be affected by many problems. There are in the stage of adolescence, the students are having numerous issues which could not be solved by them effectively. Result of this, they are drowning in the mal adjusted behaviour. This may be due to the lack of Emotional Maturity or Stability, Hormonal problems and so on. The investigator realised that if the resilience is developed among the b.ed teacher trainees, they may be in position to manage the situation and to cope up these problems ahead. Hence, the investigator, focussed as a first step of her initiation, she felt that the resilience among the students of higher education may be studied.

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Objectives

- 1) To find out the level of Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees
- 2) To find out the significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of gender.
- 3) To find out the significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of major subject.

Hypotheses

- 1) The level of psychological resilience and emotional intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees is average
- 2) There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of gender.
- 3) There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of major subject.

Methodology

The survey method was taken and target population is the B.Ed. teacher trainees who are studying in college of education in and around Karaikudi. The size of the samples of the present study is 100 B.Ed. teacher trainees. Population: The population for the present study consists of B.Ed. Teacher trainees of College of Education. Sample: The sample for the present study consists of 100 B.Ed. Teacher trainees studying in college of education in and around karai kudi. The investigator adopted the purposive sampling technique to select the respondents. Tool Used for the Study: Resilience and Emotional Intelligence Tool to be developed and validated by the investigator. Statistical Technique Used: Calculating mean, median, standard deviation and 't' test.

Hypothesis: 1

The level of Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainee is average.

Table 1 The level of Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees is Average

Variable	Low		Moderate		High		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Resilience and Emotional Intelligence	32	32	52	52*	16	16	100	100

*Indicates the level of Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of Teachers.

Finding

In regard to the B.Ed. teacher trainees 32% have low level, 52% of them have moderate and 16% of them have high level of Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of gender.

Table 2 Difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees in terms of gender

Variable	Gender	No.	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' value	Table value at 5% level	Remarks at 5% level
Resilience	Male	27	91.11	6.796	4.42	1.98	S

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and Emotional Intelligence	Female	73	90.52	5.585			
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(At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.98)

NS - Not significant (Null hypothesis accepted)

S - Significant (Null hypothesis rejected)

Since the calculated „t“ value (4.42) is greater than the table value (1.98) at 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of gender” is rejected.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of Major subject.

Table 3 Difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees in terms of Major Subject

Variable	Major subject	No.	Mean	Standard deviation	Calculated 't' value	Table value at 5% level	Remarks at 5% level
Resilience and Emotional Intelligence	ARTS	46	90.26	5.285	5.15	1.98	S
	SCIENCE	54	91.04	6.416			

(At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.98)

Since the calculated „t“ value (5.15) is greater than the table value (1.98) at 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between Resilience and Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees in terms of major subject” is rejected.

Conclusion

The statement of the study for the researcher was ‘Influence of Resilience on Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. teacher trainees’ The main findings of the study indicates that the resilience influences the emotional intelligence.

Reference

- [1] <https://blog.campusgroups.com/campusgroups/2021/5/25/strategies-to-build-student-resilience>
- [2] Sehwat A.& Simon S. (2021). Emotional Intelligence and Resilience among Young Adults. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(2), 1835- 1841. DIP:18.01.182.20210902, DOI:10.25215/0902.182
- [3] Montgomery, J. M., Schwan, V. L., Burt, J. A. G., Dyke, D. I., Thorne, K. J., Hinds, Y. L., ... & Kohut, C. S. (2008). Emotional intelligence and resiliency in young adults with Asperger's disorder: Challenges and opportunities. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 23(1), 70-93.

OPPORTUNITIES AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF KERALA

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Abstract

The present study tries to investigate the opportunities and attitude towards Continuous Professional Development (CPD) among primary school teachers of Kerala. It also tries to find out if there is any significant difference between the opportunity and attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers with respect to the district, section (L.P and U.P) and gender. The current research followed a correlational cross sectional research design under quantitative research methods. The sample consists of 600 primary school teachers from six districts of Kerala. Continuous Professional Development Status Assessment Scale was used to collect data. The data was consolidated and tabulated for further analysis. The descriptive analysis, Pearson's Correlation, t-test and One-Way ANOVA were used to analyse data. IBM SPSS version 2.0 was used for the same. The study's findings shed light on a number of significant aspects regarding the state of CPD programmes prevailing in Kerala. The analysis demonstrates the importance of bringing about substantial changes in the attitude of teachers as well as providing more opportunities to primary teachers in different parts of the state.

Introduction

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is universally recognised to be fundamental to the development of individuals and their professions. CPD for teachers is becoming increasingly relevant in countries all over the world. Day's (1999) definition of CPD includes any behavior which bring about considerable impact on classroom change. According to him "Professional development consists of all natural learning experiences and those conscious and planned activities which are intended to be of direct or indirect benefit to the individual, group or school, which contribute, through these, to the quality of education in the classroom. It is the process by which, alone and with others, teachers review, renew and extend their commitment as change agents to the moral purpose of teaching; and by which they acquire and develop critically the knowledge, skills and emotional intelligence essential to good professional thinking, planning and practice with children, young people and colleagues throughout each phase of their teaching lives" (Day, 1999, p.4). According to Guskey (2000; 2002), professional development initiatives often attempt to improve three things: teachers' classroom practices, educators' attitudes and beliefs, and pupils' learning outcomes. In India, it is "quite usual to see CPD associated with in-service training programmes...one-off, isolated, short-term, and irregular training activities," according to a report conducted by the British Council (2013). Because of the narrow definition of CPD as INSET, only official INSET programmes are recognised and supported, whereas other types of CPD, such as attending conferences, obtaining extra qualifications, or building learning communities, are often not recognized (Bolitho and Padward, 2015). It emphasises that CPD encompasses a wide range of goals and is not only confined to in-service training programmes. NCFTE (2009) and NEP (2020) made some recommendations that might be very useful in enhancing the current state of CPD. The recommendations made by National Education Policy (2020) highlight the relevance of reviewing and refining the prevailing trends in teacher professional development. Professional learning activities or programmes based on teachers' own aspirations and initiatives are not identified or supported in the majority of schools in India, which only formally recognise and support those professional development activities that have been approved, governed, and managed by the central and state governments (Padwad & Dixit, 2013). Kerala, the state renowned for its quality of public education has ranked at the forefront among the states in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals consistently by the Niti Aayog. It is in this context that the investigator wanted to get an insight about the status of Continuous Professional development programmes in the state. Since CPD encompasses both self driven and system providing opportunities, the attitude and perception as well as the breadth and width of the opportunities must be assessed. The potential for learning and growth provided by self-directed professional development is determined by the interaction of three key components: (1) the individual teacher and their personal characteristics, attitudes, and motivation; (2) their personal, social, and cultural contexts; and (3) the nature and quality of professional development opportunities available (Mercer, Farrell & Freeman, 2022). Despite the fact that educational stakeholders expect teachers to

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refine their practices and thereby enhance student outcomes as a result of their professional development, academics have done little to explore teachers' attitudes and views about such learning. The National Achievement Survey of 2017 and other research findings highlighted the demand for CPD in context of the NEP 2020's emphasis of the increasing need for high-quality education.

Objectives

- 1) To study the opportunities and attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers of Kerala
- 2) To find out if there is any significant difference between the opportunity and attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers with respect to the district, section (L.P and U.P) and gender

Hypotheses

- 1) There exists a significant association between opportunities and attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers of Kerala
- 2) There is a significant difference between districts in opportunities and attitude among primary school teachers of Kerala
- 3) There is a significant difference between section (Lower Primary and Upper Primary) in opportunities and attitude among primary school teachers of Kerala
- 4) There exists a gender difference in opportunities and attitude among primary school teachers of Kerala

Method and Measures

The current research followed a correlational cross sectional research design under quantitative research methods. The sample consists of 600 primary school teachers from six districts of Kerala (Male=160; Female=440) which is selected using stratified sampling technique. Head teachers, specialist language teachers, physical, art and work education teachers were excluded. Continuous Professional Development Status Assessment Scale (Rachana and Meera, 2020) was used to collect data. The scale consists of two parts – Part A and Part B. Part A covers the statements related to the different CPD opportunities provided by central and state departments, other agencies, schools etc. Part B includes statements to assess the attitude and perceptions of teachers towards the different opportunities they receive. It mainly included items related to the self-initiative professional development activities. The researcher ensured prior permission from the teachers concerned. Before administering the tool, sufficient instruction was given which helped teachers fill the tool effectively. Fixed time was provided to complete the tool and the researcher herself collected the filled response sheets. The data was consolidated and tabulated for further analysis. The descriptive analysis, Pearson's Correlation, t-test and One-Way ANOVA were used to analyse data. IBM SPSS version 2.0 was used for the same. Informed consent and confidentiality were ensured during the data collection process.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 Statistical Constants for the Distribution of Scores of Opportunities for CPD and Attitude towards CPD in the Total Sample and Subsamples based on Districts, Section and Gender of Primary School Teachers of Kerala.

Sample		N	Opportunities (Mean & SD)	Attitude (Mean & SD)
Total Sample		600	88.21 (12.12)	127.65 (10.85)
Districts	Wayanad	100	86.79 (12.45)	126.32 (11.09)
	Malappuram	100	88.65 (12.28)	129.66 (11.68)
	Palakkad	100	85.15 (11.59)	124.83 (11.12)
	Thrissur	100	90.05 (12.08)	128.43 (9.62)
	Idukki	100	88.44 (12.36)	126.79 (10.11)
	Kollam	100	90.19 (11.40)	129.86 (10.66)
Section	LP	300	88.23 (12.04)	128.11 (11.06)
	UP	300	88.19 (12.22)	127.19 (10.63)
Gender	Female	440	88.08 (12.13)	127.66 (10.88)

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	Male	160	88.56 (12.12)	127.66 (10.88)
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Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the variables in the total sample and subsamples, like district, section and gender. It is evident that among six district Kollam has highest value in opportunity, 90.19 (SD=11.40) and attitude, 129.86 (SD=10.66). It indicates that primary teachers in Kollam district have more attitude towards CPD as well they have more opportunities to engage in CPD programmes. Palakkad district has the lowest value in opportunity, 85.15 (SD=11.59) and whereas Wayanad district has the lowest value, 126.32 (SD =11.09) in attitude towards CPD. The table vividly points out while considering the opportunity for CPD, primary teachers in Palakkad district receive less opportunities. From the table it is also clear that lower primary teachers receive more opportunities for CPD (M =88.23, SD = 12.04) than upper primary teachers (M =88.19, SD =12.22). With regard to the attitude towards CPD, the teachers working in lower primary section show more attitude (M=128.11, SD =11.06) than upper primary teachers (M =127.19, SD =10.63). In the subsample of gender, the table clearly indicates that male primary teachers get more opportunities (M =88.08, SD =12.13) than female teachers (M =88.08, SD =12.13). In the meantime the male and female primary teachers have equal attitude towards CPD (M =127.66, SD=10.88)

Table 2 Relationship between Opportunities for CPD and Attitude towards CPD among Primary School Teachers

Variables	(1)	(2)
Opportunities for CPD (1)	-	-
Attitude towards CPD (2)	.455**	-

**p<0.01

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation test was performed to find out the relationship between Opportunities for CPD and Attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers. The result shows that there exists a moderate significant positive correlation between Opportunities for CPD and Attitude towards CPD among primary school teachers (r =0.455, p < 0.01).

Table 3 Data and Results of Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Scores of Opportunities for CPD among Lower and Upper Primary School Teachers

Variables	Section	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	p-value
Opportunities	Lower Primary	300	88.23	12.036	.044	.965
	Upper Primary	300	88.19	12.220		
Attitude	Lower Primary	300	128.11	11.058	1.035	.301
	Upper Primary	300	127.19	10.625		

Table 3 shows the test result of independent sample t-test between the mean scores of opportunities for CPD among lower and upper primary school teachers of Kerala. The mean and standard deviation of lower primary and upper primary is 88.23, 12.036; 88.19, 12.220 respectively. And the t-value is 0.044 which is not significant. It suggests that there is no significant difference between lower and upper primary teachers in terms of opportunities for Continuous Professional Development. Table also indicates the test result of independent sample t-test between the mean scores of attitudes towards CPD among lower and upper primary school teachers of Kerala. The mean and standard deviation of lower primary and upper primary is 128.11, 11.058; 127.19, 10.625 respectively. And the t-value is 1.035 which is not significant. It discloses that there is no significant difference between lower and upper primary teachers in terms of attitude towards Continuous Professional Development.

Table 4 Data and Results of Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Scores of Opportunities and Attitude for CPD among Male and Female Primary School Teachers

Gender		N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t value	p-value
Opportunities	Male	440	88.08	12.131	.427	.669
	Female	160	88.56	12.115		
Attitude	Male	440	127.66	10.885	.032	.975
	Female	160	127.63	10.767		

Table 4 presents the test result of an independent sample t-test between the mean scores of opportunities for CPD among male and female primary teachers. The mean and standard deviation of male and female is 88.08, 12.131; 88.56, 12.115 respectively. And the t-value is 0.427 which is not significant. It highlights that there is no

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significant difference between male and female school teachers in terms of opportunities for Continuous Professional Development. Table also designates the test result of independent sample t-test between the mean scores of attitude towards CPD among male and female primary teachers of Kerala. The mean score of male and female teachers are 127.66 and 127.63 and that of standard deviation is 10.885 and 10.767. The obtained t-value is 0.032 which is not significant. It reveals that there is no significant difference between male and female primary teachers with regard to the attitude towards Continuous Professional Development.

Table 5 Summary of Mean, Standard Deviation and F -value of Opportunities for CPD and Attitude towards CPD among Primary School Teachers for the Total Sample with Respect to their District

Variables	District	N	Mean	SD	F	sig
Opportunities	Wayanad	100	86.79	12.45	2.613*	.024
	Malappuram	100	88.65	12.28		
	Palakkad	100	85.15	11.60		
	Thrissur	100	90.05	12.08		
	Idukki	100	88.44	12.37		
	Kollam	100	90.19	11.40		
Attitude	Wayanad	100	126.32	11.09	3.470**	.004
	Malappuram	100	129.66	11.68		
	Palakkad	100	124.83	11.12		
	Thrissur	100	128.43	9.62		
	Idukki	100	126.79	10.11		
	Kollam	100	129.86	10.66		

Table 5 shows the results of analysis of variance. Analysis of covariance analyzed the differences between districts in terms of opportunities and attitude towards CPD. It is evident that the difference is significant at 0.05 level ($F=2.613$, $p<0.05$) in opportunities and significant at 0.01 level ($F=3.47$, $p<0.01$) in attitude. The descriptive analysis suggest some relevant issues related to continuous professional development programmes. The result throws light to the need of providing more opportunities to the primary teachers in Palakkad district and Wayanad district. It also emphasizes the necessity of changing the attitude of primary teachers in Wayanad and Palakkad district and engages them more in professional development activities. The result indicates that teachers in Kollam district have more opportunity as well as attitude than teachers from other districts. It may be due to the district's proximity to the offices at SCERT, SSK, SIEMAT etc. The finding of the study is in accordance with the research conducted in this area. There aren't many choices for teachers working in rural areas to take part in in-service training. The shortage of prospects for interaction with teachers from other schools, as well as the transportation and geographic constraints, small class sizes, and the amount of teaching staff, are some of the causes of this. Due to the dearth of opportunity for learning new information and improving oneself, teachers' professionalism may be affected (Chan, 2012). Thus it is worth noting that the districts which lag behind in opportunities and attitude are the same districts viz, Wayanad and Palakkad. This finding is an eye opener to the administrators, policy makers and the implementing persons to focus their attention more in these districts. According to the result obtained from the study, it can be said that the lower primary teachers receive more opportunities to enrich themselves professionally and they show more attitude as well than that of upper primary teachers. Since the lower primary teachers are expected to teach all the subjects, they get more exposure to many teacher empowerment programmes. Any programme which is implemented for lower primary teachers will be attended by all teachers from the sections. At the same time for upper primary teachers, they teach one or two subjects so they attend programmes related to their subjects only. It is highly significant to provide more opportunities for upper primary teachers too. Since the lower primary teachers get more exposure to professional enrichment, they have more positive attitude.

As far as gender is concerned, more than female teachers, male teachers receive more opportunity to develop professionally. At the same time while considering the attitude both groups have the same attitude towards professional development programmes. Many studies (Abugulu, 2015) conducted before prove that the male teachers do receive more opportunity than female teachers. The result of correlation analysis makes it clear that CPD chances will favourably impact teachers, and there is a possibility of a good attitude toward CPD. Similarly,

if the teachers have a positive attitude towards Continuous Professional Development, they can find out more CPD opportunities. Many researches on professional growth have been undertaken, revealing the problem (Avalos, 2011; Hadar & Brody, 2010; Irgatoglu, 2021). If analyzed, readiness for self-directed learning provides individuals with great learning opportunities (Fisher et al., 2001). It may be said to be a crucial component for professional growth in terms of these aspects. For teachers to take advantage of both individual and organisational learning possibilities, they must be prepared for self-directed learning.

Results of Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Scores of Opportunities for CPD among Lower and Upper Primary School Teachers suggests that there exists no significant difference between lower primary and upper primary teachers in terms of opportunities for professional development. The department of education does, in fact, provide equal opportunity for both lower primary and upper primary teachers. Because elementary education is so crucial, it is critical to assure its quality. It should be highlighted in this regard that teachers have similar opportunities to excel in their profession. The various agencies like SCERT, DIET, SSK etc. conduct programmes for both lower primary and upper primary teachers. Every year these agencies organise teacher empowerment programmes to enrich their skill, knowledge and practice. Results of Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Scores of Attitude towards CPD among Lower and Upper Primary School Teachers suggests that there exists no significant difference between lower primary and upper primary teachers in terms of Attitude towards professional development. The study reveals that there is no significant difference between male and female school teachers in terms of opportunities for Continuous Professional Development. It is true that department does not make any disintegration in providing chances for male and female teachers. When conducting programmes, both male and female teachers get equal chance to take part in actively. The result also discloses that there is no significant difference between male and female primary teachers with regard to the attitude towards Continuous Professional Development. Several studies conducted worldwide indicate this fact (Sivakumar, 2018; Divya, 2014; Torabi et. al, 2013).

Conclusion

The data results reveal that teachers in some geographical regions have less opportunity for professional development and they have comparatively low attitude towards such programmes. Besides teachers working in lower primary section have more attitude than that of upper primary sections. Likewise their attitude is also greater than teachers in upper primary. Even though male and female teachers have equal attitude towards CPD, the male teachers receive more professional development opportunities than female teachers. The correlation analysis results show that CPD opportunities will positively effect teachers, and there is a probability of a positive attitude toward CPD. Similarly, if teachers have a favourable attitude toward CPD, they might find out about more CPD options. At the same time it is noteworthy that there exists no significant difference in attitude and opportunities in terms of section (lower primary and upper primary) and gender.

Implication and Limitation

Based on the findings it is recommended that teachers should be more sensitive about professional development opportunities and they must be able to cultivate more positive attitude towards such opportunities. The administrators and policy makers shall ensure that teachers get sufficient exposure to develop professionally since the quality of teacher directly impacts the quality of education.

References

- [1] Abugulu, A. V. (2015). The attitude of teachers towards continuous professional development, the case of some selected teachers at Yendi municipality (Doctoral dissertation, University of Education, Winneba).
- [2] Avalos, B. (2011). Teacher professional development in teaching and teacher education over ten years. *Teaching and teacher education*, 27(1), 10-20.
- [3] Bolitho, R., & Padwad, A. (2015). Continuing professional development lessons from India.

FOSTERING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN INDIAN EDUCATION: AN EXPLORATION OF PRACTICES AND IMPACT

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Abstract

In the increasingly diversified and globalized culture of today, intercultural education is a crucial subject. The goal of this research paper is to investigate the present condition of intercultural education and the many methods and techniques employed to encourage pupils to appreciate and understand other cultures. The introduction of the study gives background information on the idea of intercultural education and its growth over time. After that, it looks at the situation of intercultural education right now, underlining the difficulties and possibilities for fostering intercultural understanding in the classrooms of today. The paper then presents a review of the literature on the various methods and tactics employed to advance intercultural education, such as the inclusion of various viewpoints, the improvement of intercultural communication abilities, and the development of inclusive and equitable learning environments. In addition, the literature review investigates how intercultural education affects student outcomes including academic success, cultural sensitivity and empathy, and intercultural competence. The study discovered that while teachers typically understand the need of intercultural education, they frequently encounter obstacles. The relevance of intercultural education and the need to create and put into practice successful intercultural understanding and respect-promoting initiatives are both emphasized in the conclusion. Substantially, this research paper offers a thorough analysis of the status and current approaches to intercultural education and emphasizes the significance of intercultural education in contemporary classrooms. Additionally, it offers insightful information for academics, decision-makers, and researchers on how to successfully encourage intercultural understanding and respect among students.

Keywords: *Intercultural, Approaches, Decision Making, Cultural Awareness, Implementation*

Introduction

A teaching strategy known as intercultural education encourages tolerance and understanding amongst various ethnic groups. Given how diverse and interrelated our globe is becoming, it is a crucial field of research. Through the development of intercultural competence—the capacity to interact respectfully and successfully with individuals from other cultural backgrounds—intercultural education aims to educate students to live and work in a worldwide society. The term "intercultural education" and its essential elements, such as "intercultural competency," "cultural awareness," and "cultural sensitivity," are at a broader level connected. Intercultural education can now be included into the curriculum and in the classroom. Intercultural education is a comprehensive approach to education that attempts to foster tolerance, acceptance, and understanding of many cultures, languages, and viewpoints. It is a system of education that is open to all kids and their families and flexible enough to meet their varied requirements. The foundation of this education is equality, social justice, and human rights. The goal of intercultural education goes beyond merely studying various cultures. It entails gaining knowledge on how to comprehend, value, and respect the cultural identities, histories, and experiences of every student. It comprises knowledge of the many modes in which people from other cultures display their creativity, intellect, and abilities. It involves realizing that there are various cultural manifestations and experiences, not just one unique "culture." Understanding of various ethnicities, languages, faiths, and socioeconomic backgrounds falls under this category. It also entails being aware of the various viewpoints, experiences, and requirements of various people within a culture. The globe is growing more varied and interdependent. The movement of people, ideas, and cultures across boundaries as a result of globalization has increased the need for intercultural understanding and communication. In this regard, education is essential in preparing students for both life and employment in a varied community. Intercultural education is a method of teaching that aim to encourage respect, acceptance, and understanding of many cultures, languages, and viewpoints. It is a system of education that is open to all students and including their families and flexible enough to meet their varied requirements.

Benefits of Intercultural Education

- 1) Students and society at large can gain much from intercultural education. It assists pupils in gaining the information and abilities needed to function in and prosper in a diverse society. Additionally, it fosters in them a growth in tolerance, empathy, and open-mindedness.
- 2) Improved Cross-Cultural Communication: Intercultural education assists students in acquiring the information and abilities necessary to interact successfully with individuals from other cultures. This

entails gaining knowledge of various communication practises, mannerisms, and nonverbal signs as well as developing the capacity to comprehend and value various viewpoints.

- 3) Increased Tolerance and Understanding: Intercultural education encourages an increase in one's tolerance for and comprehension of other cultures. It enables pupils to see the diversity among civilizations and to comprehend that there are several cultural manifestations and experiences rather than a single "culture."
- 4) Increased Empathy: By exposing pupils to other viewpoints and experiences, intercultural education aids in the development of empathy in students. This makes it easier for them to relate to and comprehend people from all origins and cultures.
- 5) Improved Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Abilities: By exposing students to other viewpoints and approaches to issues, intercultural education aids in the development of students' problem-solving and critical thinking skills. This may encourage children to develop more creative and flexible ways of thinking.
- 6) Increased Career Opportunities: Students may benefit from intercultural education by having an advantage in the labor market. Employers are increasingly searching for employees who can work well with people from diverse backgrounds and who are culturally competent.

Intercultural Education Implementation

An all-encompassing and integrated strategy is necessary for the implementation of intercultural education in schools. It entails the creation of regulations, plans, and procedures that support inclusiveness and variety of culture. This comprises:

- 1) Designing Curriculum: Making inclusive, flexible curriculum that meets the various requirements of every learner. This entails embracing ideas and viewpoints from many cultures as well as encouraging analysis of cultural concerns.
- 2) Professional Development: Providing teachers and staff with the information, abilities, and attitudes necessary to establish a welcoming and fair learning environment.
- 3) Participation in the Community: Promoting and encouraging participation in the community in schools. This involves including families, local businesses, and cultural organizations into the educational process.
- 4) In order to ensure that all children feel valued, respected, and protected, safe and inclusive settings must be created. This entails addressing issues of prejudice, bias, and discrimination as well as fostering an environment of respect and acceptance.

In conclusion, intercultural education is essential in today's increasingly multicultural and international world. It aids in fostering respect, tolerance, and understanding for various cultures and viewpoints, which can result in more harmonious and inclusive societies. Additionally, intercultural education may equip students for employment in a globally integrated workforce where the capacity to collaborate well with people from many backgrounds is becoming more and more crucial. Intercultural education should be included into the educational system at all levels and should provide chances for contacts with individuals from different backgrounds in addition to classroom learning in order to fully reap its advantages.

References

- [1] Banks, J. A. (2018). *An Introduction to Multicultural Education* (6th ed.). Pearson.
- [2] Gudykunst, W. B. (2018). *Bridging differences: Effective Intergroup Communications* (5th ed.). Sage.
- [3] Hofstede, G. (2017). *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions and Organizations across Nations* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- [4] Jackson, J., & Rudzinski, J. (2019). *Intercultural Communication: Globalization and Social Justice*. Sage.
- [5] Kim, Y. Y. (2019). *Communicating with Strangers: An approach to Intercultural Communication* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- [6] Pedersen, P. (2018). The five faces of oppression. In P. Pedersen (Ed.), *Multiculturalism as a Fifth Face of Oppression* (pp. 1-24). Routledge.
- [7] Steiner-Khamsi, G., & Waldow, F. (Eds.). (2018). *The Handbook of Comparative Education*. Springer.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Inclusive education is an educational setup where children with diverse learning needs are accommodated in the general classroom and have equitable opportunities for quality education.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, General Classroom, Learning Environment.*

Introduction

Inclusive education is concerned with removing all barriers to learning, and with the participation of all learners vulnerable to exclusion and marginalization. It is a strategic approach designed to facilitate learning success for all children. Inclusive education has become an international concept, implemented in various formal schooling systems in nations in the southern and northern hemispheres. As appropriations of inclusive education appear across the globe so do multiple meanings. In particular, cultural, historical constructions of disabilities guide context-specific implementation and policy formation of inclusive education in different countries. Disabilities seen solely as intra-individual traits lead to lowered expectations, thus constraining opportunities to learn. However when caregivers, educators, family members, and other providers understand disabilities as an intersection of social, cultural, historical, environmental, and intra-individual abilities, more equitable forms of education emerge for all students. Shifts in understanding the locus of disability guide the development of national policies and laws to support inclusive education implementation. Research has also surfaced the complexities, challenges, and innovative practices that must be considered in order to install inclusive education as a normative practice. To support inclusive education, educators need to have both the capacity to provide learning opportunities to all students in their classrooms as well as the vision that all students, regardless of race, language, religion, gender, and ability should be given the opportunity to receive an excellent education. Educators need institutional contexts that are designed to accommodate inclusive practices, and school leaders who understand the complexities of the work and can provide the feedback, support, and leadership necessary for sustaining inclusive practices across generations of students and their teachers. This article outlines the history of inclusive education and provides insight into its multiple meanings. In particular, citations are included that address the ways in which disability has been constructed.

Meaning of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is defined as a learning environment that promotes full personal, academic and professional development of all learners irrespective of race, class, color, gender, disability, sexual preference learning styles and language.

Definitions of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education may be defined as children with disabilities are education in the same classes as all the other children. "Inclusive education implies all young learners, young people's with or without disabilities beings able to common pre-school and school with an appropriate network of support service". UNICEF (2010), "Inclusion is really about how well child-friendly schools are doing at making practical changes so that all children, regardless of their background or ability, cansucceed." Understanding inclusive as a continuing process , encouraging the participation of all student's teachers and parents. Making curriculum flexible, according to the needs of the disabled, whilekeeping the objects of education the same for the child's .Providing support for the teachers aswell as the students.

Needs and Importance of Inclusive Education

Differentiated Instruction: All students learn differently and their individual needs should betaken care of. This is more so important for students with disabilities. Teachers meet everyone's needs by presenting lessons in different ways and using **Universal Design for Learning (UDL)**. One key teaching strategy is to break students into small groups. By using small groups, teaching can be tailored to the way each student learns best. This is

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known as differentiated instruction.

Reduced Stigma: Stigma is a strong feeling of disapproval that most people in a society have about something. In developing nations, there is a stigma towards people with disabilities. Inclusive classrooms are filled with diverse learners. This lets students talk about how everyone learns in their own way, thus developing understanding about each other's strengths and weaknesses. They may find that they have more in common with other kids than they thought. This can go a long way in reducing stigma for students with learning and attention issues. It can also help them build and maintain friendships. Inclusion in schools goes a long way in helping remove the negative stigma in society towards disabled people.

Effective Use of Resources: In more traditional special education settings, many students are provided related services, like speech therapy or for other specialized instruction. An inclusion class often brings speech therapists, reading specialists and other service providers into the classroom. These professionals can provide information and suggestions to help not just disabled students, but also to abled students. A non-inclusive classroom usually has the usual subject teacher that don't provide anything special to the students.

Basis for Inclusive Society: A society that embraces and integrates an inclusive education will naturally introduce the same culture of inclusion in its concepts of civic participation, employability and community relationships. The seeds of inclusion need to be planted in the young students so that they will learn the values, skills and knowledge to include others who are different from them. Those with disabilities can become pioneers of public projects and programs.

Human Resource Capitalization: If one of the motivation for uplifting women's education was to make the best use of a nation's work force, the same logic can be applied to students with disabilities. Like any minority group, disabled people can also reach their maximum potential with additional help. Through Inclusion policies in the education system, a country can expand its workforce by creating individuals who may be disabled through unfortunate circumstances but fully able and functional in productivity.

Better Academic performance: Research has shown that students learning together in the class room improves academic excellence. Students set higher expectations for themselves due to the presence of others with diverse abilities. Students with disabilities challenge themselves to perform optimally like their classmates, while other students also spontaneously set a high standard for themselves.

Development of leadership skills: Students in an inclusive education environment naturally learn to take up the responsibility of caring for one another. There are situations where students stand up and speak up to protect their friends who are bullied. This naturally can lead to a leadership skill. The school environment also encourages self-discovery as students with diverse abilities find themselves performing roles and functions they usually would not be exposed to if they had been separated.

Parental Involvement: Parents participation in the education of the child in an inclusive system can ultimately define its success. Inclusive education involves coming up with innovative and strategic methods of getting parents involved and noticed by children in the learning process. The process of creating educational contents and other learning activities in an inclusive system ensures a significant contribution of parents through the planning stage. Parents can be actively involved in their child's education and other school activities.

Building Self Esteem and Self Worth: Attending classroom settings that depict the true nature of the similarities and differences that exist in the world helps children appreciate diversity. It is essential that a child's education introduces him/her to the reality of the world out there beyond the walls of just an academic environment. Playing and learning alongside with other children of different cultures and abilities assist children to grow in understanding people that are unique in skills due to physical, social or other challenges. The culture of respect for one another also grows when children are allowed to play with one another without segregation.

Economical: Most developing nations like India have problem of funding in education. There is a lack of schools as well as teachers. By converting schools into inclusive schools, we not only save the expense of constructing a new establishment, but also get to retain the experienced staff. However, the existing staff will require additional training, which despite its additional cost, is still more economical in the long term.

Curriculum of Inclusive Education

Curriculum which takes into consideration and caters for the diverse needs, previous experiences, interests and personal characteristics of all learners. It attempts to ensure that all students are part of the shared learning experiences of the classroom and that equal opportunities are provided regardless of learner differences.

Inclusive Teaching

Hockings (2010) defines inclusive teaching as a range of intentional strategies that "engage students in

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learning that is meaningful, relevant and accessible to all.” The University of Michigan offers a more detailed explanation of inclusive teaching that emphasizes the importance of identifying how systemic inequities and bias influence learning: “Inclusive teaching involves deliberately cultivating a learning environment where all students are treated equitably, have equal access to learning, and feel valued and supported in their learning. Such teaching attends to social identities and seeks to change the ways systemic inequities shape dynamics in teaching-learning spaces, affect individuals’ experiences of those spaces, and influence course and curriculum design.” Inclusive teaching practices are beneficial for all students and can be applied in any discipline, field, or teaching and learning context. Incorporating inclusive teaching practices requires planning, ongoing reflection, and revision, and will help instructors to create welcoming and productive learning environments.

Advantages of Inclusive Education

The following are some advantages of inclusive education: Inclusive education helps every child fulfill their educational needs. It helps students with special needs gain a plan tailored to their specific needs. This helps them learn as per their capabilities in the best possible way. Disabled students often suffer from low self-esteem issues. Due to their differences and their disabilities, they feel they lack in things that their non-disabled peers have been blessed with. Inclusive education helps special-needs students understand the real world. It helps them become aware of those with unique physical and social skills and appreciate the diversity.

Conclusion

Inclusive education is about giving children, regardless of gender, community, capability, or disability, the chance to learn together. It means giving every child the right to education, to experience classroom activities, and to interact with other children and teachers in regular schools. It helps children learn that they are accepted and appreciated despite their differences. It also instills in them the confidence that they, too, can make a difference in society. Inclusive education, thus, helps remove the stigma surrounding disability and sensitizes others about the needs of special students. Implementing this principle needs careful planning, creativity, and the right resources to make it a success. But it goes a long way in teaching children the importance of looking beyond individual differences and being prepared for life in society as adults.

Reference

- [1] <https://inclusion-international.org/resource/inclusive-education> Inclusive education (researchgate.net)
globalindianschool.org/blog-details wideeducation.org

A STUDY OF THE ATTITUDE OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FOR GENDER EQUITY EDUCATION

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Abstract

Indian society still has a serious problem with gender discrimination. Women have been reduced to second-class status in the home and at work due to traditional patriarchal practices. This has a significant impact on women's political participation, financial security, education, and health. Depending on the situation, gender disparity in education can take many different shapes. Despite the fact that gender disparity disadvantages both men and women equally, girls and women nevertheless experience it more frequently. In order to learn more about the attitudes of the higher secondary students toward gender equity, to gauge their comprehension of the problem, to identify the primary causes of the issue, and to suggest potential solutions in the wake of findings, the researcher conducted a survey of 240 students in the city's higher secondary schools. A Likert scale was used to gather information on students' attitudes regarding gender equity. The role of women in society, at work, at home, and in education was one of the parameters used to understand the respondents' attitudes. Results indicated a shift in adolescents' attitudes from previous decades, although further improvement is still required. Changes in how people view women are required. Only if women are treated equally and are not denied their rights would human civilization be at its most advantageous. Therefore gender equity must be recognized as a development priority. This should address and reflect the priorities of marginalized women/girls in all areas against gender specific injustices.

Keywords: *Attitude, Gender Equity Education*

Introduction

Gender equality means that the extraordinary conduct, aspirations and needs of women and men are taken into consideration, valued and favored equally. It does not mean that women and men have to emerge as the identical, however that their rights, duties and possibilities will now not depend upon whether or not they're born male or female. Gender equity means fairness of treatment for women and men, according to their respective needs. This may encompass equal treatment or treatment that is distinctive however that is taken into consideration equal in terms of rights, blessings, responsibilities and opportunities. Depending on the situation, gender disparity in education can take many different shapes. Despite the fact that gender disparity disadvantages both men and women equally, girls and women nevertheless experience it more frequently. Poverty, geographic isolation, minority status, disability, early marriage and pregnancy, gender-based violence, and conventional views of women's status and role are some of the barriers that prevent women and girls from exercising their right to participate in, complete, and benefit from education. Gender inequality in society generally has several manifestations, with gender-based discrimination in education being one of them.

Indian society still has a serious problem with gender discrimination. Women have been reduced to second-class status in the home and at work due to traditional patriarchal practices. This has a significant impact on women's political participation, financial security, education, and health. Women from different castes, including dalit women, frequently marry young, give birth young, and are then saddled with onerous domestic and financial responsibilities. They also frequently experience unsafe abortion, child marriage, domestic violence, and male dominance in household and health decisions. State wise attendance rates as recorded by the NSS, 2004-05 are highlighted separately for male and female children of 6-14 age group .According to this data, girls in certain states (e.g. Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh) are less likely to be enrolled in school than girls in some other states (e.g. Kerala, Himachal Pradesh, Mizoram) (Bandyopadhyay M & Subrahmanian R, 2008) [1]. Generally family members inside the family network and within the society drastically impact the capacity of girls to get right of entry to services, nutrients, immunization, healthcare (in particular during bouts of contamination) and training. The best news, however, is that if women do reach college and are able to pass the preliminary barrier, they're extraordinarily stimulated and struggle in opposition to all odds to stay in faculty (Ramachandran V, 2001) [2]. [3]Das DK & Biswas R (2006) studied on 'gender inequality among adolescents in participation of activities for self-development in rural west Bengal' Researcher concluded that the distinction is probably a mirrored image of the socio-culturally decided conventional roles of the boys and girls in the households. Participation in the family sports through the woman is almost a customary phenomenon, specifically

in rural India.

The urgent need to confront these challenges is the reason for investing in adolescence. Adolescents are often considered the next generation of actors on the social and economic stage; therefore all societies would benefit from harnessing their energy and skills. Adolescents are as worthy of care and protection as young children, and as worthy of consideration and participation as adults. Now it is the right moment for the world to recognize both what it owes to them and the singular dividends that investing in this age of opportunity can generate – for the adolescents themselves and for the societies in which they live (UNICEF 2011) [4].

Research Design

Method: The research is a quantitative study based on the survey method. In this direction, the researcher conducted a survey on the 240 students of higher secondary schools of the Ujjain city. **The objectives** of this paper were (i) to find attitudes of higher secondary students with regard to gender equity, (ii) to analyze gender disparity in the higher secondary students in school education, (iii) to investigate how the current educational system affects students' awareness of gender equity. **Sample:** Students of eleventh and twelfth class of higher secondary schools of the city were selected randomly for the survey. **Measurement Tool:** A survey questionnaire is prepared to assess the attitude of the students toward gender equity. The survey structure consisted of questions based on the various situations they faced and observed in their daily life, their school, their class, at home and at work place. An attitude scale based on Likert scale was used to measure student's attitude and awareness towards gender equity. To measure student's attitude and awareness, a Likert scale type questionnaire, ranging from 1 ("Strongly disagree") to 5 ("Strongly agree") was applied. The length of the cells determined below: From 1 to 1.80 represents (strongly disagree), from 1.81 to 2.60 represents (do not agree), from 2.61 to 3.40 represents (true to some extent), from 3.41 to 4.20 (agree), from 4.21 to 5.00 represents (strongly agree).

Data Interpretation and Analysis

Results obtained from Likert scale ratings are shown in Table 1 below. This represents all the questions as items from number 1 to 10 and their ratings in the front. Graphical representation of the data is presented in the graph1 below:

Table1. Likert scale result of participants' attitude ratings

Questionnaire Item	Likert scale Ratings
A person should be friendly to other people (Whether it is male or female) working in the office.	3.8
A person should wish all his colleagues in the morning and evening irrespective of gender it belongs.	4.0
Equality in the true sense of the world does not mean to be considered the same but to be treated in similar fashion.	2.8
Adarsh feels that only those who struggle can achieve success, whether it is a girl or a boy does not have on effect on the work.	2.2
Sita believes that a man should not avoid working in the kitchen simply because he is a man and a lady is wasting her time if she tries to work in the office.	2.8
Maria is of the opinion that women must rise and revolt against the discriminatory treatment given to them.	3.5
Danish believes that we are all human beings and we should behave in a civilized manner by broadening our outlook, changing all wrong perceptions and giving due respect to all individuals. This is our true respect to god.	2.7

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It should not be appreciable that ‘Real boys’ never wash clothes or dishes and ‘real girls’ never climb trees.	3.1
You don’t like when Uma’s mother said that only girls play with dolls and only boys play with model cars.	3.5
You do not believe that women cannot do things that man can do. They are fit to cook and give birth to children.	2.7

Graph 1. Likert scale result of participants’ attitude ratings

Higher ratings on 2 questionnaire items (Item 1, and 2), suggested a positive attitude towards gender equity. Students showed their concern to respect everyone irrespective of their gender. Researcher assumed that this is due to coeducation in the schools where all students learn and grow together. Gender wise separation of the educational institutes should not be encouraged. The priority should be given to humanity. Average ratings on item 6, 8, 9 suggested a lack of information about gender disparity in the society they live in. They showed that they had the information but failed to apply it. They were unaware about the direct relation between gender equity and quality of life. Lowest ratings of item 4 suggested less awareness about struggles faced by boys and girls in every field of life. They sowed discrimination in the struggles of both the genders. It can be assumed that they were treated differently by their parents at home. Girls are expected to help in household chores while boys are not. Children must be aware about completeness and functionality of the individual in relation to its natural state. Gender equity connects them with the natural environment where they grow and it is required for their holistic development. Moderate ratings of item 3, 5, 7 and 10 suggested that it is necessary to make them understand the importance of gender equity. They showed a positive attitude for gender equality, equal work and stamina as well as fitness. As boys and girls in the city are participating in all the activities in the school irrespective of their physical conditions equally though we found less participation by the girls in village schools. This result suggested making them understand the meaning of gender equality and gender equity. If they understand this at a young age, then they will be an endowment to the country as a responsible, educated, conscious citizen. In the light of the results obtained, there is a need to inculcate the value of equality among the students of higher secondary schools of both the genders.

Findings

- 1) Attitude of the students towards gender equity education was found positive. Students showed their concern to respect everyone irrespective of their gender.
- 2) They were unaware about the direct relation between gender equity and quality of life. They sowed discrimination in the struggles of both the genders.
- 3) They showed a positive attitude for gender equality, equal work and stamina as well as fitness.
- 4) Students were found to have information about gender disparity in the society they live. They showed that they had the information but failed to apply it.
- 5) There is a need to develop the current educational system more to provide gender equity education to the future generations.

Conclusion

When we talk of developing values among our children, we emphasize on the effective objective of education i.e. the development of the social, moral aesthetic and spiritual sides of man's personality (Shukla RP, 2004) [5]. Result of the study indicated a positive attitude of the students toward gender equity and equality and this is the demand of the present scenario where we can see girls are equally finding opportunity in every field of their life. But the scene is not the same for all; not only women but men also from backward communities and areas, illiterate background, and laborer class are not embracing the same opportunities. [6] Zine J (2006) suggested allowing a deeper understanding of how gendered religious identities are constructed in the schooling experiences of the youth. [7] Hickey MG and Stratton M (2007) explained in their article on 'schooling in India: Effects of gender and caste' that despite India's free and compulsory education plan for all children up to the age of 14, a significant percentage of rural Indian children do not complete school. The present generation is passing through turbulent times. Increasing degree of discontent, frustration and unhappiness has swamped the conduct and behavior of the people all over and in every walk of life. We are living in an age in which vast technological changes have led to widespread transformation in social and cultural conditions. To cope up with these complex situations, adolescents need to be transformed through gender equity education and adjusted according to the situations in their life as well as family and society.

Future Implications

Results of the study revealed that students have a positive attitude with regard to gender equity. This study was limited to higher secondary students only. For the development of responsible societies towards gender equity, it is recommended to include primary, middle and high school students from villages also in the future studies. For broader perspective, school teachers and under-training education students should also be included in the research to develop the innovative pedagogies for gender equity education for future generations.

References

- [1] Bandyopadhyay M & Subrahmanian R (2008). Gender Equity in Education: A Review of Trends and Factors, Create Pathways To Access, Research Monograph No 18: 1-29.
- [2] Ramachandran V (2001) Reaching the Hardest to Reach, Reflections on DPEP. In: Ramachandran,V., Shukla, S., Cohen, P., Alexander, R. and Mercer, M., Reflections on Equity, Quality and Local Planning in the District Primary Education Programme, Occasional Paper. New Delhi: European Commission.
- [3] Das DK & Biswas R (2006). Gender Inequality among Adolescents in Participation of Activities for Self-Development in Rural West Bengal. Indian Journal of Community Medicine, 31 (1): 44-45.
- [4] UNICEF (2011). The State of The World's Children 2011: Adolescence an Age of Opportunity, A report by UNICEF, retrieved from http://www.unicef.org/adolescence/files/SOWC_2011_Main_Report_EN_02092011.pdf.
- [5] Shukla RP (2004). Value Education and Human Rights, Sarup & Sons, New Delhi, p.6.
- [6] Zine J (2006). Unveiled sentiments: gendered islamophobia and experiences of veiling among muslim girls in a canadian islamic school. Equity & Excellence in Education, Routledge, 39 (3): 239-252.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

TEACHER COMPETENCIES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Teaching competencies are the knowledge, understanding, application and skill that help a teacher be successful in teaching and get desired learning outcomes. To enhance the overall development of a child, the teacher must have expertise in different dimensions of teaching aptitudes so they can deal with every student having different learning capacities and styles. Segregated or Integrated education hampers the progression of a nation in many ways. To ensure the development of a country like India, an inclusive setup of education is the only way. But to fulfil the goal of inclusive education, competent teaching faculty is of the utmost importance. The readiness of family, community, and society is an important part of inclusive education. But the readiness of school and teachers are vital. In this study, the factors affecting inclusive education and teachers' role to understand and solve the problems of children with special needs have been addressed. The attitude of teachers towards inclusion will either promote or disturb the process and so all the obstacles that can negatively affect inclusion should be eradicated to enable it to nurture and flourish. Teacher competencies for an inclusive classroom or all that goes with it cannot be exhausted here thus the study continues.

Keywords: *Segregated Education, Integrated Education, Inclusive Education, Children*

Introduction

Inclusion or inclusiveness is not an easy task for a society which has many shades of beliefs, backgrounds and backwardness. Beliefs come from culture, caste, creed, religion etc. Background differs for education, economy, etc. The idea of inclusiveness is really essential for a country like India. In general, inclusiveness means the practice or policy of providing equal access to opportunities and resources for people who might otherwise be excluded or marginalized, such as those having physical or intellectual disabilities or belonging to other minority groups (Definition from Oxford Languages). General people in an average society consider those people as exceptional or rather say abnormal who depart from the general peoples' way of thinking, doing, producing, communicating or living. Psychological, physical, social, economical deviation gives birth to segregation. It is over several decades, the perception of inclusive education was defined and argued with respect to the special education viewpoint in most countries. Most commonly it is thought that inclusive education is meant only for disabled or retired children. If the amount of disabled children in India is counted it is alarming and to be more specific, it is about 36 million, which is even more than the total population of so many countries of the world. The fundamental cost and investment of teaching or rehabilitation pupils with psychological disabilities or physical deformities are huge. But this investment or separate infrastructure does not assure the output, guaranteeing a sustainable and overall development of the nation.

Segregation/ Special Education: Here children with special needs are educated at special schools with isolated infrastructure, set-ups and systems.

Integrated Education: Here children with special needs attend special classes or units or syllabi in mainstream schools.

Inclusive School: Here overall system, set-up and infrastructure has been changed to meet students' needs. Children with special needs learn effectively in mainstream schools.

GS: General Students

CWSN: Children with Special Needs

The figure describes the concept of a Segregated, Integrated and Inclusive Education system. The major

problem of the Segregated and Integrated system of schooling is, special and segregated infrastructure makes children more dependent to the simulated situation. After completion of their schooling, in many cases, they find a mismatch with the real society. It becomes a burden for society as well as the nation. There are many arguments regarding the inclusive schooling system. The most common argument is special needs children hamper general or high IQ students' development. Therefore, they need to be stayed and educated separately. This approach needs a change. A nation is made by its individuals. Each and every individual is separately important for a nation. Schooling is the process of creating a human resource for the nation obeying and focusing on its constitution, aims and objectives. Among the whole population, it's the aim of the educational sector, it is necessary to ensure a maximum number of children grow as a proper human resource of the nation. Segregation of the number of children hampers this goal. Factors Affecting Inclusion: A well-known quote in this context is much more appropriate "change the environment to suit the child, not the child to suit the environment". The greatest barrier to inclusive education is the environment or more specifically a mediocre mentality society rather than the medical impairment of an individual. A negative attitude towards differences and special situations creates discrimination and leads to severe problems and barriers to inclusion in education. Some not-so-truly educated and stereotyped people believe that children with special needs cannot be safe reliant and responsible citizens and cannot be a 'human resource' for the nation.

In India, on the basis of caste, creed, colour, gender, religion society is divided and scattered. In this society, a large number of people suffer the prejudice that children with special needs, especially with some kind of disability, are not suitable to mix with their children. It's a belief, not only of the parents or guardians but also the mediocre teachers think that if special needs children will study together, general students will lack behind in this competitive world. Poverty and mismanaged wealth are also important factors in India affecting inclusive education.

Understanding Disabled and Differently abled learners: In the context of learning, proper diction and language play an important role. Addressing is the base of communication, and communication is the base of learning. The term 'disabled' or 'handicapped' denotes a state of negativity. It focuses on deformity, disadvantages, disability, discrimination. The term 'differently abled' focuses on the ability, possibility, positivity, privilege of an individual with a special situation for special needs. Every teacher should first understand that being disabled or handicapped is a serious situation for an individual when he or she is completely dependent on somebody or a group of skilled people. But, if individuals are educatable and the possibility to be self-dependent is visible, then addressing them as disabled or handicapped is similar to committing a sin. Teachers are the key to success in an inclusive education system. Thus they need to be sensitive to the needs of students and society. They should practice the term differently abled instead of disabled or handicapped.

Preparation for Inclusive Education: The fundamental criteria for inclusive education is to prepare the school environment for equity and quality of education. It is one of the most important global phenomena today to support and help young children reach their full developmental potential and engage in lifelong learning. School readiness plays a vital role in this context.

Six obvious questions arrive here.

- 1) Are children entering school with the minimum competencies essential to retain in school?
- 2) Are children entering school with the minimum social skills essential to retain in school?
- 3) Are children entering school with the cognitive skills needed to achieve success in school?
- 4) Are schools ready with equipment to provide an inclusive environment for the children?
- 5) Are families ready to provide an optimal learning environment?
- 6) Are communities and society ready for children with special needs?

"Child is a problem in Integrated Education, System is a problem in inclusive education" is the most appropriate quote for the preparation for inclusive education. Importance of Teacher: Infrastructure is definitely needed. But, without competent faculty, every toil will stay in vain. First of all, a thorough rectification of approach and practice is needed. In a common scenario, to most of the faculties, children with special needs are a problem for the institution and for the general students. This poisonous approach is really harmful to schools as well as society. The child is not a problem, instead, the conventional system is the problem, which needs a drastic change.

Assessment of children with diverse needs is essential for a teacher in inclusive schools. A few examples of the practice, like MDPS: Madras Development Programming System; BASIC-MR: Behavioural Assessment Scale for Indian Children; FACP: Functional Assessment Checklist for Programming; VSMS: Vinland Social Maturity Scale; DDST: Denver Development Screening Test; UDPS: Upanayan Developmental Programming System and few more, are essential for a competent teacher in inclusive setup.

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Fulfilling Constitutional Responsibilities: All the government and non-government organizations, most importantly educational sectors ought to execute their responsibility to obey and teach the new generation to obey constitutional laws and regulations by accepting them and implementing them in practice. Indian constitution through many clauses and amendments has formulated, recommended and strengthened individuals' right to education. The main objective has been to universalize education by making Primary Education Compulsory or recommending the Right to Education, Education for All or special provisions for disabled and marginalized groups etc.; and providing all citizens with the opportunities to attain optimum development through education. Inclusive education is to fulfil its constitutional responsibility by gathering all groups of children to learn together and gradually from that practice to live together and to build a nation of integrity.

Recommendations for Teachers of Inclusive Schools

In an inclusive system, infrastructure is essential but the teacher is paramount. The teachers should

- 1) Change their approach from conventional to contemporary.
- 2) Practice ITC and helpful resources and devices like Graphic Calculators, Pen-top Computers, Sounding Board, Interactive Whiteboards etc.
- 3) Practice helpful software like Inspiration, Audacity, Word Prediction, Speech-to-text, Tech Matrix, Voice Thread etc.
- 4) Become a member of UNC's centre for Literacy and Disability Studies, Learning NC etc.
- 5) Research and practice on Cascade Model, Salamanca report etc.
- 6) Learn and practice the basics of braille and sign language.
- 7) Subscribe to some channels of DIY Tutorials so that they can easily make helpful and attractive TLMs.
- 8) Read and create interesting and influential motivational stories.

Conclusion

The relevance of teacher competencies in inclusive education classrooms cannot be overstressed. An inclusive curriculum is nothing without its application in the classroom, and thus the teacher plays the most important role. This is because no matter how wonderful an inclusive curriculum may be if there are no competent teachers who can manage and carry it out accordingly, the curriculum remains only a document for the archive. Quality teachers training for inclusive education is central to inclusive management and equitable teaching and fostering a broadened concept of inclusive education. Teacher competencies help the management of the potential of the children with special needs, for the future, and for the teacher himself. Therefore, teachers should note that learning how to manage or provide instructions in the inclusive classroom setting does not only play in the accumulation of knowledge and skills but in utilizing them for better teaching for the good of the special needs child. Teachers ought to have the positive mentality to try new and verified skills without anxiety so that they are able to act as agents of change to fulfil the objective articulated in the Salamanca philosophy of inclusion. When teachers are skilled in communicating information to parents, children and audience, it helps the understanding of instructions that the teacher tried to pass across and enable children to be able to articulate the meaning, and limitation and they themselves will be able to apply the information to their learning situations.

References

- [1] Abba, U. M., & Rashid, A. M. (2020). Teachers' competency requirement for implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 60-69.
- [2] Agbenyega, J. (2007). Examining Teachers' Concerns and Attitudes to Inclusive Education in Ghana. *International Journal of whole schooling*, 3(1), 41-56.
- [3] Ainscow, M., Slee, R., & Best, M. (2019). the Salamanca Statement: 25 years on. *International Journal of inclusive education*, 23(7-8), 671-676.
- [4] Bukvić, Z. (2014). Teachers competency for inclusive education. *The European Journal of Social & Behavioural Sciences*.
- [5] Das, A. K., Kuyini, A. B., & Desai, I. P. (2013). Inclusive Education in India: Are the Teachers Prepared?. *International journal of special education*, 28(1), 27-36.

MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION: A PRESENT NEED OF INDIA

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Abstract

India has a wide range of cultural traditions. A pattern known as "unity in variety" represents the multicultural experience. This great cultural variety is always at odds with fair representation and acceptability as a member of society. This includes the diversity of religious communities, languages, regionality, and minority populations in each of the states and regions that comprise the country, but these diversities are also organically connected. The notion of diversity is crucial, but it also represents an opportunity for India's peaceful and progressive future. As a result, appreciating variety and multiculturalism becomes critical. Such ideals can take strong roots if they are instilled in a student's life from the start. Instilling intercultural ideas in pupils is a common objective of educational curricula. When these concepts are incorporated into educational materials, they can have beneficial consequences. The Indian education system has long been concerned with the difficulty of meeting the demands of tremendous learner variety. Because of increased regional mobility, schools in India are facing a more diversified population than ever before, making it critical for school educators to implement changes that match the requirements of the kids. Multicultural education may help kids see themselves and others who are different but yet part of the same system. However, there are several impediments and difficulties to overcome these issues. This paper aims for the clear identification of the barriers and the tentative solutions that teachers can use for the removal of those hindrances but, firstly there should be an in-depth understanding of multicultural education. This will lead us to the barriers to multicultural education and finally the tentative solutions can be suggested for teachers which can help in better equipped to survive in today's fast-changing world.

Introduction

India is a culturally varied country, and these differences must be considered. Culture and multiculturalism are inextricably linked. Culture is one of the distinguishing features of human society. Every civilization has its own culture, yet it is now clear that society is made up of people from many cultures. Culture is the deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, social hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relationships, concepts of the universe, and material objects and possessions acquired by a group of people in the course of generations through individual and group striving. (Samovar & Porter, 2001, p. 8) The Swiss coined the word "multiculturalism" in 1957 to describe their country's four spoken languages and several religions. According to the notion of multiculturalism, no individual or society should be judged only based on three distinct languages and cultures. Multiculturalism is that all cultures should be treated with equal respect and acknowledgement. The education system in India symbolises and supports secular and democratic ideas. As a result, it is a mash-up of numerous civilizations rather than a single one. Education has a critical part in passing down this culture from generation to generation. As a result, Indian multicultural education is founded on social justice, educational fairness, and respect for different points of view.

Multicultural education encompasses any type of education or instruction that combines the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and viewpoints of persons from many cultural origins. It is critical to developing an atmosphere that can successfully assist students' learning while responding to the demands of diverse pupils from various cultural backgrounds. It is based on the premise of educational equity for all students, regardless of cultural background, and it attempts to remove obstacles to educational opportunity and achievement for students from diverse cultural backgrounds. Texts and learning materials in schools may integrate diverse cultural viewpoints and allusions. Teachers may learn about their students' cultural origins and then add learning experiences and information that are relevant to their cultural viewpoints and history. Multicultural education includes content integration, the process of constructing knowledge and wisdom, bias reduction, equitable pedagogy, and empowering school culture and social culture. It allows pupils from many ethnic groups to converse and connect. Multicultural education incorporates the idea that all students – regardless of their gender, social class, and ethnic, racial, or cultural characteristics – should have an equal opportunity to learn in school” (Banks and Banks 2010 p. 3)

The Barriers to Multicultural Education

Multicultural education arose from the civil rights movement's quest for political power, liberty, and economic integration in the 1960s. Various oppressed and subjugated groups urged that cultural and ethnic content be included in public schools at the time. (Banks, 1989). As a result, feminist groups fought for this sort of educational reform in the late 1960s and early 1970s, urging educational institutions to give educational opportunities and jobs to people of colour. Schools and other educational institutions rushed to address these issues and modify the standard curriculum. Throughout the late 1960s and early 1970s, these efforts aided in the early idealisation of multicultural education. (Gay, 1994).

In the 1980s, James Banks, one of the pioneer scholars of multicultural education, examined schools as social systems in a multicultural society. Multiculturalism is "A philosophical position and movement that deems that the gender, ethnic, racial, and cultural diversity of a pluralistic society should be reflected in all of the institutionalized structures of educational institutions, including the staff, the norms, the values, the curriculum, and the student body" (Banks, 2005).

This philosophical premise served as the foundation for his concept of multicultural education, to ensure that every kid, regardless of social affiliation, had an equal chance for education. As a result, multicultural education was both the means and the end objective for achieving equitable goals.

Multicultural education has faced several hurdles since its inception, but studies done around the turn of the century reveal that these impediments are becoming more prevalent. According to a summary, the most significant hurdles that multicultural education instructors face today are as follows:

- 1) Ethnicity,
- 2) Inequality,
- 3) Different Ways of knowing,
- 4) Different learning styles.

Barrier 1: Ethnicity

Ethnicity has been highlighted as one of the primary barriers to effective teacher-student contact and communication in a multicultural education system. Previous research employed several "indicators" to assess the influence of ethnicity on students' views. Some of these factors were the state of birth of parents and pupils, "the length of residency in the state or area," and the "language spoken at home." In 2005, Den Brok and Levy's research on the influence of students' and teachers' ethnic origins on three areas were reviewed: (1) how students perceive their instructors' behaviour, (2) how teachers treat individual students, and (3) students' accomplishment. The authors found that if ethnicity is not addressed appropriately by instructors, it can have major consequences for both interaction and accomplishment. Then, in multicultural education, the impact of ethnicity on both students' and instructors' opinions is critical. To put it another way, instructors must be aware of the function of ethnicity in the classroom to minimise detrimental effects on the teaching-learning process.

Barrier 2: Inequality

The serious impact of inequality in multicultural education, students of reserved categories were considered "problematic," they were not allowed to sit in the same classroom with upper caste students, they were not allowed to drink water from the taps in the schools that all students and teachers were allowed to drink from. However, during the last two or three decades, schools have become more "culturally responsive," and instructors have begun to take pupils' cultural differences and "equity" into account. Surprisingly, despite all attempts, it has been determined that inequality "is continuing" as a fundamental impediment to intercultural education. In the author's opinion, Changing the curriculum, implementing alternative programmes, educating teachers "for culturally diverse schools," and adjusting the focus of teacher preparation research can all contribute to improved outcomes in the future. (Sleeter, 2001).

Barrier 3: Different Ways of Knowing

The tremendous effect that culture has on people's "ways of knowing" or epistemologies. Rothstein-Fisch and Trumbull (2008), assert that each culture influences how individuals know and learn. These "means of knowing" include "how humans arrange their reality cognitively through language and other sign systems". It also involves how individuals "approach learning and problem-solving, how they create knowledge and how they pass it on from generation to generation. People's diverse perspectives result in distinct methods of knowing. Several studies show that when a teacher is uninformed that multicultural education is not homogenous and addresses the

pupils as if they all had the same "ways of Knowing," some of his/her students get disoriented and less motivated. As they find themselves in a learning environment that is different from how they have been socialised in their homes and communities, these students frequently acquire emotions of inferiority and carelessness.

Barrier 4: Learning Styles

The significance of knowing students' learning patterns in multicultural education, for example, "Context speaks to the student's culture. Individually or in groups, how do they learn best? What cultural perspectives do they offer, and what style of classroom best reflects that culture? What function does socialisation play in their culture?" In Gay's (2002) study, most instructors, it is believed, have just a cursory understanding of their students' learning styles. Teachers' misunderstanding of these cultural variables is frequently caused by their knowledge sources: "What individuals believe they know about the area is frequently founded on shallow or incorrect information supplied by popular culture, mass media, and critics."

Tentative Solutions

Although educating pupils from a foreign culture is risky. One of the most important criteria of intercultural education is that teachers modify their old ways of thinking. Teaching pupils ought to promote "justice" and "equity". The recommendation for instructors to eliminate these impediments is to change the emphasis from "student weaknesses" to "student talents," independent of linguistic or cultural background. This can assist teachers in focusing on "knowledge building" while reducing bias and prejudice. Serious steps must be done at the training level to prepare teachers for intercultural education. "If students are taught in colleges and universities that continue to respect just the knowledge and contributions of people in society, they will have restricted perspectives to offer to their teaching." Today, school transformation is the most important prerequisite for effective teaching in multicultural education. Better student accomplishment will not be accomplished until fundamental educational reforms with a multicultural focus are implemented.

Conclusion

The primary goal was to identify the major hurdles and potential solutions required to effectively instruct pupils in intercultural education. Teaching kids from diverse origins is a difficult endeavour for any instructor. Teachers "cannot be expected to do miracles" as they "can't teach in which they are having difficulty". When a teacher enters a classroom with students from diverse cultures, he or she enters a minefield in which the language, kind of interaction, the material presented, and method of assessing pupils must all be carefully considered. Ignoring or underestimating pupils' language and cultural differences is likely to result in classroom confusion or misinterpretation. These characteristics, in turn, may result not only in major confrontations between teachers and students but also in a poor assessment of the student's genuine level.

References

- [1] Banks, J. A. (1993). Multicultural education: Historical development, dimensions, and practice. *Review of Research in Education*, 19, 3-49. doi:10.2307/2F1167339
- [2] Banks, J. A. (2013). The construction and historical development of multicultural education, 1962–2012. *Theory into Practice*, 52(1), 73-82. doi:10.1080/00405841.2013.795444.
- [3] Banks, J. A., & Banks, C. A. M. (Eds.). (2010). *Multicultural education: Issues and perspectives*. (7th ed.) Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [4] Den Brok, P., & Levy, J. (2005). Teacher–student relationships in multicultural classes: Reviewing the past, preparing the future. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 43, 72–88. doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2006.03.007.
- [5] Gay, G. (2002). Preparing for culturally responsive teaching. *Journal of Teacher Education*, (53)2, 106-116. Retrieved from http://mrc.spps.org/uploads/preparing_for crt- _geneva_gay-2.pdf.
- [6] Rothstein-Fisch, C., & Trumbull, E. (2008). *Managing diverse classrooms: How to build on students' cultural strengths*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD. Samovar, L. A. & Porter, R. E. (2001). *Communication between cultures*. Belmont: Wadsworth Publishing Company.

EFFECTS OF CIRCUIT TRAINING AND BATTLE ROPE TRAINING ON EXPLOSIVE POWER OF SCHOOL GIRLS

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to find out the effects of circuit training and battle rope training on explosive power of school girls. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty school girls from M. Deivanai Achi Government Girls Higher Secondary School, Paganeri, Sivaganga District, Tamilnadu were selected as subjects. The selected subjects' age ranged from 11 to 13 years. The selected subjects were equally divided into three groups, i.e. two experimental groups and one control group. The experimental group-1 was allotted to circuit training (CT); the experimental group-2 was allotted for battle rope training (BRT) and group-3 acted as control group (CG). The explosive power was chosen as a dependent variable; it was tested by standing broad jump. The test was taken before and after the training interventions. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the significant difference, if any among the groups. In order to find out superiority effect among the groups, the Scheff's Post Hoc test was used. The level of significance was 0.05. After the six weeks training interventions improved the nature of explosive power.

Introduction

Now a day's fitness is considered as most important health indicators in childhood. The concept of physical fitness has since evolved to include morphological and metabolic components. (Sutha, Maniazhagu, 2019) During the early stages of strength training, especially with entry-level athlete almost any strength training method or program will result in strength development to some degree (Maniazhagu, Malar, Manogari, 2019) Children and young people are now recommended to take part in at least 60 minutes of moderate to vigorous physical activity daily to promote and protect healthy heart function, increase bone and muscle strength, improve mood and lower the risk of depression and reduce the risks of obesity, osteoporosis and diabetes (Malar, Maniazhagu, 2020) Different training methods have been commonly used to improve physical fitness and related standards of performance of athletes. (Maniazhagu, 2010) During recent years, the circuit training program is a form of exercise that has become widely used. (Davis et al, 2011) Circuit training is often erroneously portrayed as an intensive and stressful form of exercise, with a drill sergeant type in the middle of a circuit bellowing orders at weary recruits. This system produces positive changes in motor performance, general fitness, muscular power endurance and speed. (D. Maniazhagu, C.Robert Alexander and Sukumar Sha, 2011). The circuit training effectively reduces the time devoted to training while allowing an adequate training volume to be achieved (Alcaraz Ramon et al. 2008). Moreover, it permits a greater motor engagement time (Lozano et al., 2009). Strength training is a long-term intention. Trainees do not achieve the peak performance immediately after the four to six weeks of training. But relatively during the competitive phase, which is months away from the anatomical adaptation phase. (Sridhar, Maniazhagu, 2018)

Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study thirty school girls from M. Deivanai Achi Government Girls Higher Secondary School, Paganeri, Sivaganga District, Tamilnadu were selected as subjects. The selected subjects' age ranged from 11 to 13 years. The selected subjects were equally divided into three groups, i.e. two experimental groups and one control group. The experimental group-1 was allotted to circuit training (CT); the experimental group-2 was allotted for battle rope training (BRT) and group-3 acted as control group (CG). The explosive power was chosen as a dependent variable; it was tested by standing broad jump test. The test was taken before and after the training interventions. The training approach was taken for the period of six weeks, five days in a week.

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Results

Table – I The Results of Analysis of Covariance on Explosive Power of Different Groups (Scores in Meters)

Test Conditions		Ex-1 CT	Ex-2 BRT	Gr-3 CG	SV	SS	Df	MS	'F' ratio
Pre test	Mean	1.08	1.08	1.06	B	0.002	2	0.001	0.43
	S.D.	0.05	0.05	0.03	W	0.06	27	0.002	
Post test	Mean	1.31	1.3	1.04	B	0.46	2	0.234	52.0*
	S.D.	0.09	0.04	0.03	W	0.12	27	0.005	
Adjusted Post test	Mean	1.31	1.30	1.05	B	0.44	2	0.22	48.13*
					W	0.12	26	0.005	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence. The required tables value for test the significance was 3.35 and 3.37 with the df of 2 and 27, 2 and 26.

Results of Explosive Power

The pre test mean and standard deviation on explosive power scores G1, G2 and G3 were 1.08 ± 0.05 , 1.08 ± 0.05 and 1.06 ± 0.03 respectively. The obtained pre test F value of 0.43 was lesser than the required table F value 3.35. Hence the pre test means value of circuit training; battle rope training and control group on explosive power before start of the respective treatments were found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27. Thus this analysis confirmed that the random assignment of subjects into three groups were successful. The post test mean and standard deviation on explosive power of G1, G2 and G3 were 1.31 ± 0.09 , 1.3 ± 0.04 and 1.04 ± 0.03 respectively. The obtained post test F value of 52.0 was higher than the required table F value of 3.35. Hence the post test means value of circuit training and battle rope training on explosive power were found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27. The results proved that the selected two training interventions circuit training and battle rope training was produced significant improvement rather than the control group of the sample populations. The adjusted post test means on explosive power scores of G1, G2 and G3 were 1.31, 1.30 and 1.05 respectively. The obtained adjusted post test F value of 48.13 was higher than the required table F value of 3.37. Hence the adjusted post test means value of circuit training and battle rope training on explosive power were found to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 2 and 26. The results confirm that the selected two training interventions namely circuit training and battle rope training on explosive power were produced significant difference among the groups. In order to find out the superiority effects among the treatment and control groups the Scheffe's post hoc test were administered. The outcomes of the same are presented in the table I (a).

Table - I (A) the results of scheffe's post hoc test mean differences on explosive power among three groups (scores in meters)

Ex-1 CT	Ex-2 BRT	Gr-3 CG	Mean Differences	Confidence Interval Value
1.31	1.30		0.01	0.1
1.31		1.05	0.26*	0.1
	1.30	1.05	0.25*	0.1

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

Result of Scheffe's Post Hoc test on explosive power

Table I (a) shows the paired mean differences of circuit training, battle rope training and control group on explosive power. The pair wise comparisons results as follows. First comparison: Group 1 and Group 2: The pair wise mean difference of group 1 and group 2 values 0.01 was lesser than the confidential interval value of 0.1. Hence the first comparison was insignificant. The results of this comparison clearly proved that both training have produced similar effect on explosive power. Second comparison: Group 1 and Group 3: The pair wise mean difference of group 1 and group 3 values 0.26 was higher than the confidential interval value of 0.1. Hence the

second comparison was significant. The results of this comparison clearly proved that circuit training has produced significant improvements on explosive power, than the control group. The adjusted post test mean deference of experimental and control group value graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1 The adjusted post test mean values of experimental and control groups on explosive power

Discussion on Findings

The aim of the study was to compare the effects of circuit training and battle rope training on explosive power. The findings of the study showed that the circuit and battle rope training produced similar effects on explosive power. The following earlier studies are in line with the present study findings. V.Senthil Kumar and Maniazhagu (2014) found that the twelve weeks of circuit resistance training improved the ability of motor fitness variables in college students. Chen, WH, Wu, HJ, Lo, SL, Chen, H, Yang, WW, Huang, CF, and Liu, C (2018) found that the battle rope training effectively improves the multiple physical fitness and shooting accuracy in basketball players. Muktamath, D Maniazhagu, Muktamatha, Basavaraj (2010) investigated a study on two modes of resistance training, they found that the after the 8 weeks of training intervention produced significant improvement on speed, leg explosive power, anaerobic power. Manal Azab (2019) investigated a study on battle rope exercises on power and leaping ability in rhythmic gymnastics. They found that the 10 weeks of battle rope training resulted to increase power and leaping ability for female college students. KS Sridhar and Maniazhagu (2018) investigated a study on explosive strength and strength endurance based circuit training. They found that the explosive strength based circuit training improved the nature of explosive power. Senthil kumar and Mohammed Abdul Kaddafi (2021) conducted a study to find the effects of low intensity circuit training and high intensity circuit training. They proved that the eight weeks of low intensity circuit and high intensity circuit produced significant improvement on explosive power.

Conclusions

After the six weeks of training interventions the ability of explosive power was improved in both circuit and battle rope training. In between the training groups, the training effect was similar.

References

- [1] Chen, WH, Wu, HJ, Lo, SL, Chen, H, Yang, WW, Huang, CF, and Liu, C (2018). Eight week battle rope training improves multiple physical fitness dimensions and shooting accuracy in collegiate basketball players. *The journal of strength and accuracy in collegiate basketball players*.
- [2] Debbie Lawrence, Richard (Bob) Hope (2015). *The Complete Guide to Circuit Training*. A&C Black Publisher.
- [3] Dr.D.Maniazhagu (2010). "Effects of two modes of resistance training on speed leg explosive power and anaerobic power of college men students", *Indian Journal for research in Physical Education and sports sciences*, October 2010-March 2011, 31-34
- [4] J. N. Davis, L. E. Gyllenhammer, A. A.Vanni, M. Meija, A. Tung, E. T. Schroeder, D. Spruijt-Metz, and M. I. Goran, "Startup circuit training program reduces matabolic risk in Latino adolescents," *Medicine & Science in Sport & Exercise*. April 2011, pp. 2195-2203.

VIRTUAL REALITY FOR HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

Virtual reality (VR) technology has the potential to revolutionize education by providing a more immersive and interactive learning experience. This technology can be used to create virtual environments that simulate real-world situations, allowing students to engage with the material in a more holistic and meaningful way. VR can also be used to create interactive simulations that allow students to apply their knowledge and skills in a safe and controlled environment. By using VR in education, students can learn at their own pace, in a way that is tailored to their individual needs and learning styles. Additionally, VR can facilitate collaboration and teamwork, as well as provide students with access to resources that may not be available in traditional classroom settings. Overall, VR has the potential to enhance the effectiveness of education and improve student engagement and learning outcomes.

Introduction

Virtual reality (VR) can be defined as a realistic computer-generated environment that immerses the user in a simulated reality through sensory stimulus. Virtual reality can be derived from the meanings of 'virtual' and 'reality'. Virtual refers to something almost tangible, while reality is what we experience as human beings. Therefore, the phrase 'virtual reality' essentially conveys the notion of 'near-reality'. We were taught in school that we have five senses: taste, touch, smell, sight and hearing. Apart from our five traditional senses, we possess many more. We have a sense of balance, for instance. Our brain can take in sensory inputs from the environment and process them to ensure a constant supply of information. Our senses are the only way to understand our reality. Our brains process the sensory information we receive and create a collective experience of what is real. This amalgamation of sensory details and sense-making by our brains constitutes our perception of reality. Consequently, we may experience a version of reality which doesn't exist but appears genuine from our viewpoint.

Virtual reality can help provide a more immersive and interactive learning experience for students, which can lead to a more holistic education. For example, VR can be used to create simulations of real-world scenarios and environments, allowing students to explore and learn about subjects through hands-on and in an engaging way. Additionally, VR can be used to create virtual field trips, allowing students to visit places that they may not be able to visit in person. This can help to increase student engagement and understanding of the material being taught. Furthermore, VR can also be used to create interactive learning activities, such as games and quizzes, which can help to make learning more fun and engaging.

Virtual reality for Holistic Education

Holistic education is an approach to education that focuses on the development of the whole person, rather than just focusing on academic achievement. It aims for the fullest possible human development enabling a person to become the very best or finest that they can be and develop fully 'those capacities that together make up a human being' (Forbes, 2003). This approach emphasizes the importance of developing the student's physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being. Holistic education is student-centered and emphasizes the importance of the individual student's unique needs and interests.

Some key elements of holistic education include:

- 1) Developing Critical thinking and problem-solving skills
- 2) Promoting Emotional development
- 3) Encouraging Social development
- 4) Emphasizing the importance of ethical and Moral development

This approach aims to create well-rounded and balanced individuals who are able to think critically, communicate effectively, and lead fulfilling lives. It also aims to create a learning environment that is inclusive, supportive and empowering.

VR for Critical Thinking

Critical thinking is the ability to analyse and evaluate information in order to make well-reasoned decisions. It involves the use of logic and reasoning to identify the strengths and weaknesses of arguments, and to separate facts from opinions. Virtual Reality (VR) has the potential to enhance critical thinking skills by immersing users in simulated environments that simulate real-world scenarios. Problem Based Learning assisted by Augmented Reality books improve students' critical thinking skills (Saphira and Prahani, 2022). By placing users in simulations that require them to solve problems and make decisions, VR can help users develop their critical thinking skills in a number of ways:

- 1) **Problem-solving:** VR allows users to practice solving problems in a safe and controlled environment. This can help users develop their ability to analyze information, identify patterns, and make logical decisions.
- 2) **Decision-making:** VR can also help users practice making decisions by simulating real-world scenarios. This can help users develop their ability to weigh the pros and cons of different options and make well-informed decisions.
- 3) **Perspective-taking:** VR can also help users develop their ability to see things from different perspectives. This can help users think more critically about their own beliefs and assumptions and consider alternative viewpoints.
- 4) **Experimentation:** VR allows users to experiment with different options and see the outcomes, providing them with the possibility to learn from their mistakes and make better decisions.

Some examples of VR apps that can help develop critical thinking skills include

- 1) "Keep Talking and Nobody Explodes" - a cooperative game that requires players to work together to defuse a virtual bomb
- 2) "The Lab" - a collection of mini-games and experiments that require players to think critically and solve puzzles
- 3) "Tilt Brush" - a painting app that allows users to create 3D art in a virtual environment
- 4) "Cosmoscope" - A VR app that allows users to explore and understand complex scientific concepts in an interactive way.

VR for Emotional Development

Emotional development refers to the way in which a person learns to understand and express their emotions, as well as how they respond to the emotions of others. It is a complex process that occurs throughout a person's lifespan. Virtual reality (VR) can be used to support emotional development by providing immersive experiences that allow individuals to practice regulating their emotions and interacting with others in simulated social situations. For example, VR therapy has been used to help individuals with autism improve their social skills and emotional regulation. Additionally, VR can be used to expose individuals to situations that may trigger certain emotions, such as anxiety or fear, in a controlled environment, allowing them to learn to manage these emotions more effectively. A study, conducted by researchers at the University of Wollongong in Australia, found that VR can be used to teach empathy and understanding of different cultures. The study used VR simulations to transport students to different parts of the world, allowing them to experience the culture and way of life of people living in those areas. The students reported feeling more empathetic and understanding of the people they had encountered in the VR simulations, and they also showed a greater interest in learning about other cultures.

Some examples of VR apps that can help develop emotional development skills include

- 1) "Be Another Lab" - a VR experience that allows users to "swap" bodies with someone else, in order to understand and empathize with their experiences
- 2) "The Empathy Experience" - a VR app that allows users to experience life from the perspective of different people, including refugees, people with disabilities, and people living in poverty
- 3) "The Body VR" - a VR app that allows users to explore and understand the human body and its functions in an interactive way
- 4) "VR Therapy" - a VR app that allows users to experience different therapeutic scenarios and techniques in order to develop emotional regulation and coping strategies

VR for Social Development

Social development refers to the process of learning and adapting to social norms, customs and behaviours. It encompasses the development of social skills, such as communication, empathy, and collaboration that are essential for interacting and building relationships with others. The Centre for Innovative Applications of Internet and Multimedia Technologies (AIMTech Centre) at City University of Hong Kong developed a VR-enabled training program to examine its efficacy on emotional and social skills with six VR scenarios depicting the daily lives of typical children in Hong Kong and found that VR seems to be a promising asset to traditional training and therapy (Yuan and Shing IP, 2018). The study used VR simulations to help the children practice social interactions in a controlled and safe environment. The children who participated in the study showed significant improvements in their social skills, as well as in their ability to understand and interpret social cues. Virtual Reality (VR) has the potential to enhance social development by allowing users to interact with others in simulated environments. By placing users in virtual environments where they can interact with other users, VR can help them develop their social skills in a number of ways:

- 1) **Communication:** VR allows users to practice communicating with others in a safe and controlled environment. This can help users develop their ability to express themselves effectively and understand the perspectives of others.
- 2) **Empathy:** VR can also help users develop empathy by allowing them to experience life from the perspective of different people. This can help users understand and relate to the experiences of others, which is an important aspect of social development.
- 3) **Collaboration:** VR can also help users develop collaboration skills by allowing them to work with others in virtual environments. This can help users learn how to work together effectively, which is essential for social development.
- 4) **Social interactions:** VR allows users to interact with others in virtual environments, providing them with opportunities to practice social interactions in a safe and controlled environment.

Some examples of VR apps that can help develop social development skills include

- 1) "AltspaceVR" - a social VR platform that allows users to interact with others in a variety of virtual environments, such as virtual lounges, classrooms, and events
- 2) "Rec Room" - a social VR game that allows users to play games and participate in activities with other players
- 3) "Engage" - a VR platform that allows users to attend virtual events, such as conferences and trade shows, and interact with others in a virtual setting
- 4) "Spatial" - a VR collaboration tool that allows users to meet and work together in a virtual environment.

VR for Moral Development

Moral development refers to the process of learning and understanding moral and ethical principles, and how to apply them in decision making. It encompasses the development of moral reasoning, empathy and the ability to understand the perspectives of others. . In role playing and simulation, role play enhances empathy than simulation to the students through virtual reality (Olsen and Oertel, 2020). Virtual Reality (VR) has the potential to enhance moral development by allowing users to experience and interact with simulated ethical and moral dilemmas in a safe and controlled environment. By placing users in virtual environments where they can make decisions and experience the consequences, VR can help them develop their moral reasoning and decision-making skills in a number of ways:

Empathy: VR can help users develop empathy by allowing them to experience life from the perspective of different people and cultures. This can help users understand and relate to the experiences of others, which is an important aspect of moral development. **Moral reasoning:** VR can also help users develop their moral reasoning by allowing them to consider the consequences of their actions and make well-informed decisions. **Cultural understanding:** VR can also help users develop an understanding of different cultures and historical events, fostering cultural sensitivity and understanding, which are important aspects of moral development. **Ethical scenarios:** VR can allow users to experience and solve different ethical scenarios, such as medical, business, and personal ones, helping them to develop their understanding of moral principles and how to apply them in real-life situations.

Some examples of VR apps that can help develop moral development include

- 1) "The Machine to be Another" - A VR experience that allows users to "swap" bodies with someone else, in order to understand and empathize with their experiences and cultures
- 2) "The VR Museum of Fine Art" - A VR app that allows users to explore and appreciate art from different cultures and time periods, fostering cultural sensitivity and understanding
- 3) "The VR Holocaust Experience" - A VR app that allows users to learn about the Holocaust and understand the impact of discrimination and genocide on individuals and society
- 4) "Ethical Dilemma" - A VR app that allows users to experience and solve different ethical scenarios, such as medical, business, and personal ones.

Conclusion

Virtual reality (VR) can be used as a tool to support holistic education. Holistic education is an approach to education that focuses on the development of the whole person, rather than just focusing on academic achievement. This approach emphasizes the importance of developing the student's physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being. Additionally, VR technology can be used to create simulations of real-world scenarios and environments, allowing students to explore and learn about subjects in a more hands-on and interactive way. This can help to increase student engagement and understanding of the material being taught. In summary, VR technology can be used as a tool to support holistic education by providing an immersive and interactive learning experience, and by helping to develop a wide range of skills and attributes that are important for the overall well-being of the student. It's important to note that VR is still a relatively new technology, and more research is needed to fully understand its impact on holistic education. VR can provide a unique platform for holistic education by allowing students to experience different environments, cultures, and perspectives, which can foster empathy and global citizenship.

References

- [1] Astuti, T. N., Sugiyarto, K. H., & Ikhsan, J. (2020). Effect of 3D Visualization on Students' Critical Thinking Skills and Scientific Attitude in Chemistry. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(1), 151-164.
- [2] Aziz, K. A., & Siang, T. G. (2014). Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality combination as a holistic application for heritage preservation in the Unesco World Heritage Site of Melaka. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 4(5), 333-338.
- [3] Forbes, S. (2003). *Holistic education: An analysis of its ideas in nature*. Brandon, VT: Foundation for Educational Renewal
- [4] J. Black, L. C. Glazebrook, and J. R. Stutts, "Using virtual reality to improve social skills in children with autism," *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, vol. 42, pp. 2414-2424, 2012.
- [5] Kavanagh, S., Luxton-Reilly, A., Wuensche, B., & Plimmer, B. (2017). A systematic review of virtual reality in education. *Themes in Science and Technology Education*, 10(2), 85-119.
- [6] R. Gee, N. Owen, and M. Kwok, "Empathy and understanding through virtual reality," *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, vol. 25, pp. 97-108, 2009.
- [7] Radianti, J., Majchrzak, T. A., Fromm, J., & Wohlgenannt, I. (2020). A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda. *Computers & Education*, 147, 103778.
- [8] Saphira, H. V., Rizki, I. A., Alfarizy, Y., Saputri, A. D., Ramadani, R., & Suprpto, N. (2022, November). Profile of Students' Critical Thinking Skills in Physics Learning: A Preliminary Study of Games Application Integrated Augmented Reality. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2377, No. 1, p. 012088). IOP Publishing.
- [9] VillenaTaranilla, R., Cózar-Gutiérrez, R., González-Calero, J. A., & LópezCirugeda, I. (2022). Strolling through a city of the Roman Empire: an analysis of the potential of virtual reality to teach history in Primary Education. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(4), 608-618.

PORTRAYAL OF YUPPIE CULTURE IN THE NOVEL “THE GOLDEN GATE” BY VIKRAM SETH: A THEMATIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Culture has now become the most propelling and arousing subject in the dimension of the scholars. Culture is evasive but an exhaustive and inclusive term. Culture is something that evolves and sprouts out; it is not born or created. Therefore its scope and pertainment are obscurely defined. The denotation of culture in social science is wide enough to consider all human characteristics and social cohesion that are acquired and not nascent. In general non-innate societies and the variation endow to the formation of several cultures. Vikram Seth's adventurous journey towards the west made the entire globe as his home. The novel “The Golden Gate” is set in American background and especially San Francisco. His life in San Francisco makes him to picturizes the American life in a realistic manner He effectively projects the life Yuppies and urban life of San Francisco. “Yuppies” refers to the young people all over the world, who have settled in Californian society and works with high pay and high standards of Californian urban living. Vikram Seth has experienced the life style of the yuppies and has also lived among them in California. So this makes him to analyse the attitude and psychology of them.

Keywords: *Adventure, San Francisco, Yuppies, Love, Frustration, Parties, Work.*

Vikram Seth is one of the prominent Indian novelists. He has taken novels to another level by giving it a new dimension by using sonnet form for narration. His writings show his contribution towards the enrichment of Indian English novel in terms of themes and techniques. Vikram Seth is a multifaceted writer. He is a poet, novelist, travel writer, author, children's writer, biographer and also memoirist. His three novels consist of different background settings and different characters which allows the readers across the world to get to know about other countries and their culture. The novel “*The Golden Gate*” comprises of 594 sonnets written in iambic tetrameter. This narrative form was inspired from Alexander Pushkin's “*Eugene Onegin*” which is written in verse form of iambic tetrameter with the rhyme scheme “aBaBccDDeFFeGG”. The lower case letters represents masculine rhymes.

Vikram Seth being a globetrotter whose adventurous life starts from the local customs of India to life of England, China and America. So this adventurous journey towards the west made the entire globe as his home. His writings mostly deal with multiculturalism. His works shows his love towards various cultures and never compares other culture to his native culture. Leslie talks about his liking towards California as,

It is not his detachment but rather his love for California that was the most valuable to him in writing the book. One cannot come with a cold and objective eye from outside and then write affection about a place. One must have lived years in that place and just observed for years. (Mohanty 4)

The novel “The Golden Gate” is set in American background and especially San Francisco. His life in San Francisco makes him to picturizes the American life in a realistic manner and he focuses on the love relationship, gay person, depression, frustration, nuclear weapon and also towards self-acknowledgment. He effectively projects the life Yuppies and urban life of San Francisco. “Yuppies” refers to the young people all over the world, who have settled in Californian society and works with high pay and high standards of Californian urban living. In today's world, young people mostly prefer stylistic lifestyle and not traditional one. Youngsters are willing to break their norms and live according to their liking and always wanted to enjoy their life. So this leads to the loss of tradition and later on we would even forget our traditional base. The societies of the youngsters are provided with modern needs. The novel represents the life of youngsters in twentieth century. Their culture, language, food, modern gadgets and living style reflects the Californian society.

Vikram Seth has experienced the life style of the yuppies and has also lived among them in California. So this makes him to analyse the attitude and psychology of them and Seth has conveyed it to the readers in a realistic manner. The socio-cultural life in America has been portrayed in the novel “The Golden Gate” which shows his love towards California. Seth never shows his feeling of detachments from Indian society. So this makes the readers who are apart from California, can visualize and experience California through the novel “The Golden Gate”

...It was not his detachment but rather his love for California that was most valuable to him in writing the book ... One can't come with cold and objective eye from outside and then write with affection about a place. One must have lived in that place and not just observed for years. (Mohanty 135)

San Francisco became a convergence place in 1980's. Students prefer to pursue their higher

education in abroad and especially California and we also have many budding students from India to pursue their education in California. Seth has also continued his education in Oxford and Stanford after his education in India and he chooses Californian background for his novel *"The Golden Gate"*.

I thought, oh my God, thick-headed beach boys and no intellectual conversations. But then I met people who were both very intelligent and interested in things of mind and also who would think nothing about teaching you to swim butterfly. For me it was like a revelation in a wonderful way. That's why *"The Golden Gate"* in a way for all its tragedy, it's a happy book. (Knorr 40)

Seth gives the taste of Californian life and culture in the novel *"The Golden Gate"*. The life of American people was portrayed which includes various parties and celebration. He incorporates almost every culture of the Californian people which also projects friendship, love, marriage, divorce, death and work. A commentator from the Silicon Valley states:

It is a total, unparalleled pleasure to wallow in the seductive cadences of Seth's poetic novel, and then marvel at the no doubt obsessive and somewhat twisted brain which has come up with the words, rhymes and humour in this book. In the style of long long ago, this book is the only one I have ever read which brings poetry totally and absolutely to life. It is poetry which details and narrates; talks about punk rock, bands and watches love come and go. This is a great experience. (Mohanty 132)

The novel *"The Golden Gate"* reflects certain themes like alienation, separation and frustration. All these factors show the existing contemporary American society. The novel analyses the culture, tradition, living standards, mentality of the people and also the gay relationship. The novel focuses on the modern Californian society. The contemporary trend has changed the culture of California and the present generation started to live their life according to their liking. The characters in the novel were projected as spending luxurious life, various ceremonies, parties and dinners. The young society has been facing many contemporary issues like hybrid culture, restaurant, music, art and ethnicity. Seth highlights middle class society and their problems like illiterate, unemployment, divorce, frustration, loneliness and so on.

Seth not only focuses on the yuppies but also the urban side of San Francisco. The novel shows the story around September and ends on next year of November. Seth conveys almost all the happenings around San Francisco which includes the life of Yuppies in the cities and farms of the country side. This novel does not project the ideal American ethnicity because San Francisco is a land of multicultural people. Majority of the characters in the novel *"The Golden Gate"* are non-residence of America.

The novel conveys the issues of generation gap through the concept of religion and science. So the sufferings of the younger generations were also focused in the novel. The young characters in the novel are within twenty to thirty years old. So the younger generation has to adopt themselves to this socio-cultural society. They choose their profession according to their education and skills. John, the protagonist of the novel is a twenty six years old middle class man, who has studied computer science. Studying computer was considered as a fashionable one during the early twentieth century and during this period people were towards modern equipment and gadgets. So studying computer was considered as a prestigious one. But the life of John was spent in solitude and ends up in an isolated state.

John character shows the life of existentialism where he couldn't find anything useful. He couldn't even find the reason for his existence. The next character Janet Hayakawa is a friend of John and she too leads the same life as John. Her family emigrated from Japan and settled in Canada. She is highly sincere in his profession and has spent her life alone in her apartment. But she distracted herself from her worries by playing drums.

John and Jane love each other and they were living together before marriage. Both of them spent their time together at restaurants and ice-cream parlours where they chat, eat and enjoy their time together. Culture like living together is acceptable and casual in San Francisco and this relationship made their bond closer. This made John to suffocate a lot after their break up. John was in search of love and even his mother failed to show her affection towards him because she was busy in her works.

Most of the twentieth century women face such issues where they failed to balance their family and job. So John has got a mother for namesake but he also lost it when she died. Then he shifted his attention towards his father so he writes letters to his father who resides in Kent but rarely received reply letters from his father. So all this lose made John to feel isolated and never gets to mingle with the society. So he started to spend his time alone. He visits restaurants and ice-cream parlour just to see other couples spending their time together. He sometimes speaks to Jane over phone and her voice made him free from loneliness. He has also invited Jane for lunch just to spend his time with her where they talk about their day and spend some valid time. John then told Jane that it is difficult for him to get out of his loneliness, so Jane decided to find a life partner for John through matrimony. The modern society has become more advanced, through these advertisements they get to know about each other

through the information given by the individuals, so it becomes more personal between the bride and the groom. So Jane gave information about John in a matrimonial site by describing him as:

Young handsome yuppie, 26
Straight forward, sociable, but lonely
Cannot believe that he's the only
Well-rounded and well-meaning square
Lusting for love. If you, out there,
Are friendly, female, under 30,
Impulsive, fit and fun, let's meet.
Be rash.... (*The Golden Gate* 2.3)

John received eighty four replies from the advertisement. This shows the reality of the modern age, where people were attracted towards advertisement, the catchy words and never give importance to the person in reality. Not only digital advertisement, marketing also focused on the outdoor advertisements like posters in order to gain attention from non-gadgets users. But these posters diverted the attention of the drivers and even cause accident and traffic.

Liz, also known as Elizabeth Dorati is an Italian immigrant and settled in California. She has completed her studies in Law. Her parents Mr. and Mrs. Dorati are farmers. So through these characters Seth brings the country side and farmer's culture to the knowledge of the readers. Liz and John meets often, so they become closer and they started to live together before marriage. Such culture was never accepted in India but it is common to Californian people. Kilpatrick has shared his view on America in his "*From Grace to Glory: A Little Bit about Lot of Things*":

The 1980's continued the trend of the 1960's and 1970's – more divorce, more unmarried living together, more single parent families. The two-earner family was even more common than in previous decades, more women earned college and advanced degrees, married had fewer children... Materialism and self indulgence characterized the atmosphere of the 1980's as yuppie culture emerged and for elite few values was judged in house, cars and gadgets. (From Grace to Glory 121)

Seth has included few scenes based on get-together and parties. Through all these scenes Seth projects the socio-culture of San Francisco and the present condition of the younger generation. Jude Edvenson Thjomoe explains the situation portrayed in the novel, where they conduct various parties and the reason behind hosting such parties in his work "*Poetic technique in Vikram Seth's The Golden Gate*":

The first party is a cocktail party given by Liz and John. The second is a repeating 'potluck' breakfast party hosted by Phil, with neighbours and friends in attendance. A third party is a thanksgiving dinner, a family party held by the Dorati parents at their vineyard estate. The fourth party, also held in the vineyard area, is the wedding reception of Liz and Phil; and the fifth party is the party at Jan's apartment, at which John ends up playing host. (The Golden Gate 31)

References

- [1] Chhina, Arpan. Multicultural Approach and Cultural Conflict in the select novels of Anita Desai and Kiran Desai: An Analysis of *Bye Bye Blackbird* and *The Inheritance of Loss*. Lovely Professional University.
- [2] Ciftci, Hasan. Relationship between popular culture and music. *The Journal of International Management Research*, P. 178-189, April 2016.
- [3] Eshwari, M. Socio-cultural perspectives in the select novels of Vikram Seth. Thesis. Komarapalayam: Department of English, JKKN College of Arts and Science, 2018.
- [4] Kilpatrick, Naomi Ruth Jones. *From Grace to Glory: A Little Bit about a Lot of Things*. Xlibris, 2017.
- [5] Knorr, Katherine. Vikram Plays to His 'Truest Judges. *Hindu Literary Review*. 19 May 2014. Web. 21 Jan. 2016.
- [6] Mohanty, Seemita. A critical analysis of Vikram Seth's Poetry and fiction. New Delhi: Atlantic, 2007.
- [7] Seth, Vikram. *The Golden Gate*. New York: Penguin, 1986.
- [8] Thjomoe, June Edvenson. *Poetic Technique in Vikram Seth's The Golden Gate*. Thesis. Norway: The Department of Humanities, University of Oslo, 2008.

ASSESSMENT OF ACHIEVEMENT IN GRADE 8 STUDENTS IN THE SINHALA LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The study was to assess the achievement of grade 8 students in the Sinhala Language in Sri Lanka. Language skill is a vital factor influencing the achievement of students. To achieve the goals in Education the National Education Research and Evaluation Centre (NEREC) of the Faculty of Education, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka has been conducting National Assessments since 2003 in with collaboration the Ministry of Education financed by the World Bank. This study was funded by the NEREC. The main objective of the study was to determine the achievement of learning outcomes of students completing grade 8 in the year 2021 in the Sinhala Language. Thus, the test was administered in the May of 2022. Construct and validate test items to assess the achievement in expected learning outcomes in the Sinhala language of grade 8 students, Find out patterns in the achievement of grade 8 students according to their gender and school type and Find out areas of strengths and weaknesses in the achievement of grade 8 students in line with the Essential Learning Competencies (ELCs). Three parallel tests were administered and the final test was validated according to item response theory. The sample was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. It was revealed that the male performance (51.52) is lower than the female performance (57.73). And also achievement level of the male is lower than the overall mean score, while female achievement is above the overall mean value. The mean value of the students in 1AB schools is the highest. The lowest performance can be seen from the students in type 2 schools.

Keywords: *Achievement, Learning Outcomes, Grade 8 Students*

The Background of the Study

Education for All (EFA) is an international initiative first launched in 1990 to bring the benefits of education to “every citizen in every society.” To realize this aim, a broad coalition of national governments, civil society groups, and development agencies such as UNESCO and the World Bank Group committed to achieving six specific education goals: In 2000, 189 countries and their partners adopted the two EFA goals that align with Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) 2 and 3, which refer to universal primary education and gender parity. The World Bank recognizes that achieving these goals requires supporting the full EFA commitment. The Bank supports EFA through multidimensional efforts to improve educational quality and learning outcomes, Improve primary school access and equity, Improve the dropout and retention rates of girls, as well as their learning outcomes, and promote early childhood development. Therefore to achieve those goals the National Education Research and Evaluation Centre (NEREC) of the Faculty of Education, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka has been conducting National Assessments since 2003 in with collaboration the Ministry of Education financed by the World Bank. The NEREC has conducted national assessments of learning outcomes both at the primary level as well as secondary level. At the primary level, assessments were conducted at Grade 4 in 2003, 2007, 2009, 2013, and 2015. The subjects were First Languages: Sinhala and Tamil, and second National Language: English and Mathematics. At the secondary level, the National Assessments of learning outcomes were measured at Grade 8 in 2005, 2008, 2012, 2014, and 2016. The subjects were English, Mathematics and English language. The achievement of the first language was not assessed in Grade 8. Thus, it is highly essential to assess the achievement of learning outcomes of the grade 8 students.

Often the tests are the assessment tools that are used to determination of the student’s achievement relating to the cognitive domain within the quantitative research of education. Oral examinations, true-false tests, multiple-choice tests, matching tests, fill-in-the-blank exams, scales, short answer tests, written examinations, and open-ended questions are used in order to assess and evaluate the achievement of the student at all the stages and in all the fields of the education. These all test methods have superior or weak aspects involved compared to each other. However, the achievement of learning outcomes of the students depends on many factors. The intelligence of the student is one of the most important factors in achievement. Past research has shown that intelligence is a good predictor of academic success (Elshout & Veenman, 2012; Stenberg & Kaufman, 1998, Stinebrickner & Stinebrickner, 2016). Many other studies have proved that, in addition to intelligence, the personality traits of the students have a strong impact on achieving learning outcomes (Allik & Realo, 2017; Dollinger & Orf, 2021; Premuzic & Furnham, 2021).

Language skill is another vital factor influencing the achievement of students. Murray (2016) reported

that the weak language skills of students have become a problem even for Australian students. Even though the official and predominant language in Australia is English, the language skills of minority students and international students became an issue such that a national symposium was convened in 2015 by the Australia Education International (AEI) and the International Education Association of Australia. As a result of this symposium, a document on the good practice principles for English language competence for international students in Australian universities emerged. The relationship between language proficiency and academic success is well documented. Students whose language proficiency levels are not adequate to have difficulty grasping the subject matter. (Maleki & Zangani 2017). Many researchers found that students who are more proficient in the instruction language are on average more successful (Kumar, 2014; Sadegi et al. 2013). It has been argued that instruction in a non-native language creates many obstacles to student success. Students who are not fluent in the medium of instruction language that is not their native tongue have difficulty grasping course content. Therefore, assessing the achievement of the learning outcomes of the mother tongue is very essential. Thus, the assessment of the learning outcomes of the Sinhala Language will be a prominent empirical study.

Significance of the Study

Research is an information-generating activity and its result can serve as a basis for maximizing the effectiveness and efficiency of the relevant field. Students in schools have to make decisions regarding achieving learning outcomes, and co-curricular and extracurricular activities. Studies have revealed some disconcerting insights into the ways such choices are made. Therefore, this study will help the grade 8 students to identify their strengths and weaknesses in the Sinhala Language.

Learning outcomes are the cornerstones of course design and assessment, and help students focus on what is important. Learning outcomes can also be considered an inclusive teaching practice as they can help clarify expectations for all students. They make it easier for students to “know what they know”. The many benefits of using effective assessment for learning outcomes include:

- 1) Improved relationships between teachers and students.
- 2) Improved achievement.
- 3) Improved confidence, resilience, and self-esteem amongst learners.
- 4) Improved classroom culture and teaching and learning environments.

The study will reveal patterns and trends in the achievement of sub-skills of the Sinhala language. Weak areas of the sub-skills can be identified, and remedial measures can be suggested. According to the trends and patterns, further interventions can be planned.

The Main Objective of the Study

In accordance with the series of studies carried out by the NEREC related to the national assessment, the main objective of the study was to determine the achievement of learning outcomes of students completing grade 8 in the year 2021 in the Sinhala Language.

Specific Objectives of the Study

- 1) Construct and validate test items to assess the achievement in expected learning outcomes in the Sinhala language of grade 8 students
- 2) Find out patterns in the achievement of grade 8 students according to their gender and school type
- 3) Find out areas of strengths and weaknesses in the achievement of grade 8 students in line with the Essential Learning Competencies (ELCs)

Limitations of the Study

It is expected to develop four language skills in any language: Listening, speaking, reading, and writing. But this study was limited to assessing only the writing skills of the grade 8 students. The target population of the present study was limited to Grade 8 students in government schools in the Colombo district those who is medium of instruction is in Sinhala. Type 3 schools were excluded from the sample as they have classes up to grade 5. The study will be limited to 24 schools that were selected utilizing stratified random sampling. The student sample was limited to six hundred.

Sampling Methodology

The population of the present study is the students in Grade 8 in Sinhala medium classes in government schools in Sri Lanka. Looking to the wideness of the population, it is necessary to bind certain limitations.

Target Population

According to Creswell (2014), target population refers to the entire group of individuals or objects to which researchers are interested in generalizing the conclusions. Thus the target population of the study was the students who have completed grade 8 in Sinhala medium classes in government schools in the Colombo district.

Sampling Procedure

As cited by Creswell (2014) Probability sampling has a better chance of resulting in a representative sample, and according to Brink and Wood (1994:106), randomness is also associated with generalizability. Therefore random sample method was utilized for this study. Cost and time considerations have influenced the decision to limit the sample to the Colombo district, grade 8 students. In selecting the sample for the pilot test, the data analysis requirements were considered. The sampling procedure has two stages. In the first stage, twenty-four schools were selected by applying the stratified random sampling method. The stratum was the type of school. Then six hundred and twenty students who have completed grade 8 in the year 2021 were selected utilizing the same method. The stratum was gender. A questionnaire was administered to twenty-four teachers who teach the Sinhala language to the grade 8 students in the selected schools.

Construction of the Sinhala Language Paper

The test construction team comprised two university academics, ISA in Sinhala, and two teachers who teach the Sinhala language to grade 8 students. First, the team prepared a table of specifications for the following methodological procedure in preparing a test blueprint. The three parallel papers were constructed and then pilot tested in January 2021. The items for the final paper were selected after analysing the pilot test data according to the Conquest analysis. The content and face validity of the items were tested and the final paper was constructed to be administered in the first week of May 2022.

Item Selection for the Final Test Paper

The item analysis was carried out using conquest software which is based on item response theory to select valid items for the final test paper. IRT models are often referred to as latent trait models. The term latent is used to emphasize that discrete item responses are taken to be observable manifestations of hypothesized trait, construct, or attribute, not directly observed, but which must be inferred from manifest responses. The performance of an item in a test is described by the item characteristic curve (ICC). The curve gives the probability that a person with a given ability level will answer the item correctly. Persons with lower ability have less of a chance, while persons with high ability are very likely to answer correctly.

The analysis of items using IRT helps test developers to understand whether the items are successful in measuring the latent variable defined by the test and also to understand whether items tap into the same construct. The Classical Test Theory (CTT) makes inferences about a student's true score on a test. It does not generalize about the "traits levels" that the student possesses. As the CTT does not make any assumptions about the latent traits of the students, it cannot make inferences about latent traits. The IRT makes assumptions about the latent traits of students and the items are designed to tap into the defined latent variable. The Conquest provides facilities to estimate the fit statistics, item discrimination, item difficulty, point biserial correlation, item characteristic curves, item category curves, item expected curves, item information curves, etc. In terms of IRT, a good item should possess the following characteristics. Thus, the following criteria were considered in the selection of valid test items.

- 1) The fit mean square index is close to 1.
- 2) The discrimination index is higher than .4.
- 3) The point biserial correlation increases with increasing score and the point biserial correlation should be positive for the higher score category.
- 4) The average ability measure increases with the increasing score.
- 5) The observed item characteristics curve is close to the theoretical curve (ICC).
- 6) Behaviour patterns of the Distractor curves

Analysis of Data

Data gathered through the achievement test were analyzed using the conquest software and SPSS. Patterns in the achievement of learning outcomes were presented using mean, standard deviation, and cumulative percentages. Furthermore, graphs such as frequency polygons, and bar graphs were also used to present the data

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visually.

Findings

Patterns in achievement in the Sinhala Language of grade 8 students

The study was limited to the government schools in the Colombo district. First overall student achievement would be discussed about student performance in the Sinhala Language. The dispersion of marks is explained in the student cumulative percentage table given below. Achievement of grade 8 students in Sinhala Language.

Class Interval	Student Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
0-9	2.8	2.8
10-19	6.3	9.1
20-29	8.5	17.6
30-39	6.8	24.4
40-49	13.6	38.0
50-59	15.1	53.1
60-69	20.5	73.6
70-79	11.5	85.1
80-89	9.5	94.6
90-100	5.4	100.0
Total	100.00	

According to the table, the highest percentage of students (20.5%) scored between 60-69. However, the number of students who have scored above 80 marks is only 14.9%. There are 2.8 % of students who have obtained marks below 10.

Achievement Level by Gender

There is a difference between female and male in the achievement in grade 8 students. The overall mean value is 54.63. According to figure 4.2, male performance is lower than female performance. And also achievement level of male is lower than overall mean mark, while female achievement is above the overall mean score.

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Mean values according to gender- Sinhala language

The following table, elaborates on the disparities in the achievement of grade 8 students according to their gender. Cumulative student percentages according to gender.

Class Interval	Male		Female	
	Frequency Percentage	Cumulative Percentage	Frequency Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
0-9	3.33	3.33	2.33	2.33
10-19	7.33	10.66	5.32	7.65
20-29	10.33	21.00	6.64	14.29
30-39	8.00	29.00	5.65	19.94
40-49	16.33	45.33	10.96	30.90
50-59	14.67	60.00	15.61	46.52
60-69	17.33	77.33	23.59	70.10
70-79	9.33	86.66	13.62	83.73
80-89	10.00	96.66	8.97	92.70
90-99	3.33	100.00	7.31	100.00
	100.0		100.00	

According to the Table, the highest percentage (17.33%) of male students fall into the class interval 60-69. As well as the highest percentage (23.59%) of females falls into the same class interval. Even though there is only 19.94 cumulative percent of female students who have obtained below 40 marks, there is a 29.00 cumulative percent of male students who have obtained below 40 marks. There is a huge difference between the percentage of male and female students in class intervals 70-79.

Figure 4.3, graphically depicts the dispersion of marks according to gender. Dispersion of marks by gender.

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The above graph illustrates the two curves are negatively skewed. It can be concluded that there are more high achievers than low achievers among both females and males. The pattern of the two curves is slightly similar at the beginning. Then in the middle female performance is higher than male performance. Both curves become similar again at the end. For both groups, the peak of the curve is in the same class interval (60-69). However, the highest achievers among females are higher than the high achievers of males. The same pattern of scores distribution was able to identify from the national assessment conducted by NEREC. The achievement of the students in relation to the type of the school will be discussed next.

Achievement Levels by Type of School

Mean scores were calculated to compare the achievement level of the students by type of school. The differences in mean scores are graphically illustrated in the below figure.

The mean values among the school types

The students' achievement according to the school types is further significant when the mean scores are considered in the table. The mean value of the 1AB students is the highest. The lowest performance can be seen from the students in type 2 schools. Their mean score is identical to the pass mark. It shows an unsatisfactory level of achievement. This can affect to go down the overall mean values of the students. The following table indicates the disparity in achievement according to the type of school.

Class Interval	1AB		1C		Type 2	
	Frequency Percentage	Cumulative Percentage	Frequency Percentage	Cumulative Percentage	Frequency Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
0-9	0	0	3.08	3.08	7.86	7.86
10-19	1.13	1.13	7.18	10.26	15.00	22.86
20-29	2.63	3.76	11.79	22.05	15.00	37.86
30-39	3.01	6.77	8.21	30.26	12.14	50.00
40-49	12.03	18.80	14.87	45.13	15.00	65.00
50-59	15.04	33.83	14.87	60.00	15.71	80.72
60-69	29.70	63.53	17.44	77.44	7.14	87.86
70-79	13.91	77.44	10.77	88.21	7.86	95.72
80-89	14.66	92.11	7.18	95.39	2.86	98.57
90-100	7.89	100.00	4.62	100.00	1.43	100.00

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	100.00		100.00		100.00	
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Sinhala language achievement according to school type

As the above table indicates there is a considerable gap among the type of schools. In 1AB schools, the highest frequency percentage (29.7%) falls in the class interval 60-69. In 1C schools, the highest frequency percentage (17.44 %) falls in the same class interval 60-69. In type 2 schools, the highest frequency percentage

(15.71 %) falls in the class interval 50-59. Achievement in different types of schools are further illustrated through the frequency distribution graphs below.

Dispersion of marks of school type

According to the graphs, the low achievers are high in type 2 schools. It shows a positively skewed distribution. It indicates there are high amounts of low achievers than the number of high achievers. The other two curves of 1AB and 1C Schools are negatively skewed. But the achievement of 1C schools is also not satisfactory.

Find out areas of strengths and weaknesses in the achievement of grade 8 students in line with the Essential Learning Competencies (ELCs).

There are twelve competencies in the Sinhala Language and Literature syllabus in grade 8. This study was limited to measuring the competency levels of the students in the Sinhala language. Therefore the 10th, 11th and 12th competencies were excluded from preparing the test paper. The 1st and 2nd competencies were also excluded due they present the competency related to listening and speaking. Thus seven competencies and fifteen competency levels were considered. Item Facility indexes were calculated to identify strengths and weaknesses in each competency level. The following table presents the facility indexes of items 1-20 of part I of the paper and items 1 and 2 of part II of the paper. The last two items of part II are related to writing skills.

Competency Levels	Content area	Qs. No.	Facility values (Correct %)
5.2	Traditional terms and their meaning.	1	89.52
	Vocabulary	2	59.00
3.2	ඉහළ පාඨ	3	75.21
	Alphabetical order	4	37.60
3.1	Application of correct spelling rules	5	37.10
3.3	Types of letters in the Alphabet	6	38.27
6.2	Application of different types of verbs	7	54.08
	Mixed verbs	8	37.98
6.1	Types of Nouns	9	47.82
5.1	Similar words	10	40.10
	Opposite words	11	64.56
	Adjectives	12	42.43
	Words with multiple meanings	13	23.28
	Single word	14	23.46
3.2	සමානව පාඨ	15	41.83
4.1	Application of correct Punctuation marks	17	68.00
6.5	Syntax-Apply grammatical rules in writing sentences	18	63.67
		19	23.00
		20	73.83
	Part II		
9.4	Apply language to identify cultural differences.	1(i)	83.83
	Reading and comprehension-	1(ii)	89.52
		1(iii)	92.18
		1(iv)	55.07
6.5	Syntax	1(v)	53.28
1.1.2.3	Reading and comprehension- Identification of the type of the poem	2(i)	48.75
	Comprehension	2(ii)	75.87
	Identification of poetic tricks	2(iii)	44.76
	Writing the specific meaning	2(iv) a	37.93
	Writing the specific meaning	2(iv) b	63.39
7.1.3.1,4,2,6.5	Writing official letters		
		3	No single word is written
			2.00%
3.1,4,2,6.5,8.1	Writing essays	4	No single word is written
			6.3%

Student achievement in relation to competency levels

Suggestions

Low achievement of the students reveals the necessity to improve the quality of teaching procedures,

learning procedures, and assessment procedures. And all should provide opportunities for equitable quality education.

Quality Improvement for Teaching Procedure

Teaching learning procedure has been totally changed due to the Covid -19 pandemic. However, the responsibility of the teacher is to create a learner-centered environment in the teaching-learning process. With the expansion of the Humanistic Approach in education where the principle of “Every child is educable” is considered more important. Teacher training programmes, and capacity development activities should be implemented to strengthen the skills and instincts abilities of the teachers.

Quality Improvement for the Learning Procedure

A quality and equal learning environment should be provided. Action research can be implemented. Remedial intervention programs should be introduced. They should be addressed the nature, mental, social, emotional, and physical well-being of the students.

Quality Improvement for the Learning Procedure

The concept of “assessment for learning” should be implemented at the classroom level. Authenticity should be considered in conducting the assessment. Rubrics should be introduced specially for performance-based assessment.

References

- [1] Abdirahman, M., Abubakar, A. H., & Abukar, M. S. (2013). English language proficiency and academic achievement for undergraduate students in Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), 59–66.
- [2] Allik, J., & Realo, A. (2017). Intelligence, academic abilities, and personality. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 23(5), 809–814.
- [3] Anderson, Lorin W. and Krathwohl, David R. (Eds.) with Airasian, Peter W., Cruikshank, Kathleen A., Mayer, Richard E., Pintrich, Paul R., Raths, James, and Wittrock, Merlin C., *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom’s Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*, Addison Wesley Longman, Inc. 2001.
- [4] Bloom, Benjamin S. (Ed.), Englehart, Max D., Furst, Edward J., Hill, Walker H., and Krathwohl, David R., *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, The Classification of Educational Goals, Handbook I: Cognitive Domain*, David McKay Company, Inc. New York, 1954, 1956.

BARRIERS AND METHODS IN MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. At the classroom level, for example, teachers may modify or incorporate lessons to reflect the cultural diversity of the students in a particular class. In many cases, “culture” is defined in the broadest possible sense, encompassing race, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, and “exceptionality “ a term applied to students with specialized needs or disabilities. Generally speaking, multicultural education is predicated on the principle of educational equity for all students, regardless of culture, and it strives to remove barriers to educational opportunities and success for students from different cultural backgrounds. This paper focuses the barriers and methods in multicultural education in India.

Keywords: *Barriers, Methods, Multicultural, Education, Curriculum*

Introduction

Multiculturalism is cultural diversity. Multiculturalism is meant to respect different cultures and give them a constitutional equal place. No one culture in the country should become dominant to other cultures so that one may disappear. The future of any culture depends on the ideology of the educated class in that country, which means that the education system of that country effects that culture. Education is a means of cultivating, preserving and transitioning culture, so in a country like India which has adopted multiculturalism, secularism, it is imperative to inculcate multiculturalism in education to inculcate multiculturalism. India has different religions, different languages, educational backgrounds, customs, and values. Indian culture has been developed by people of many religions. The distance between the country and the people has become closer, the whole world has become a global village. It does not matter if the Constitution of India is a basic cultural document. Some of the provisions in the new education policy 2020 in relation to multicultural education are very striking. Multilingual education, which will increase investment in education from 4.43% to 6.6% of GDP, will help students to access the benefits of quality education. This is a welcome thing.

Meaning of Multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is the process of giving equal justice to all religions, people of different cultures, without any distinctions on the basis of race or culture.

Definitions of Multiculturalism

According to A. E. Barnes “Multiculturalism is a term that has come to serve as shorthand for a host of different and not necessarily related cultural and educational issues. Arguments relating to gender studies, ethnic and racial studies, affirmative action, freedom of speech on campus, compromise and corruption among educational administrators have all been aired under the title, multiculturalism”.

Barriers in Multicultural Education

Barriers to multicultural education in the curriculum implementation are hidden curriculum, the inability of teachers to implement multicultural education, etc. Finally, barriers to multicultural education in curriculum evaluation are misconception of evaluation and limited evaluation methods.

Lack of Multicultural Teaching Strategies

If a multicultural approach is to be inculcated in the students, the multicultural teaching strategy needs to be adopted by the teacher but to a large extent the multicultural teaching work policy is not followed by the teachers. Adoption of holistic teaching methods by the teacher creates interest in the students in terms of learning but most of the teachers do not appear to be doing so, making it difficult for the multicultural approach to take place in the students.

Lack of Cultural Awareness

Lack of cultural awareness creates many difficulties in building mutual cultural tolerance among students. Without culture awareness, preservation, nurture and transition of culture will not be possible. It is necessary to develop multicultural ideology in the society along with the students, it has become difficult due to lack of multicultural awareness.

Cultural Conflicts

Cultural conflict is a pre-existing conflict. Cultural conflict creates prejudices against each other's cultures. At the same time, it seeks to dominate the minority culture over the majority culture. Therefore, cultural conflict has created a huge obstacle in multicultural curriculum and cultural education.

Prejudiced Attitude

Prejudicial thinking creates negative attitudes of one group towards another, creating cultural differences. This increases the sense of superiority, destroys social harmony and creates cultural and social conflicts. Therefore, prejudiced attitudes are a major obstacle in multicultural education.

Social Inequality

Indian society is divided into different religions, castes, ethnicities, creeds, languages, genders. Therefore, it is difficult to create a sense of unity in the society. In such a situation, brotherly respect does not develop in the society. Many disadvantaged groups are aware that they are being subjected to socio-cultural and political injustice. So social inequality is an important barrier in multicultural education.

Multicultural Curriculum Teaching Methods

Project method: The project method is extremely beneficial for the proper implementation of the multicultural curriculum. It is possible to enable students to be multicultural through the project method. There are many types of projects that can be undertaken, for example, gathering information on various social issues, gathering information on different cultural features, gathering information on various environmental issues. In this way students can do innumerable projects of this kind.

Problem solving method: In a culture where there are many bad practices and traditions in every culture, by adopting problem solving methods, the teacher should give the problem projects to the students with a view to find the right solution in the context of many such bad practices, practices, traditions and find the right solution. For example, the Honda method suggests appropriate solutions to the problem, find out the causes of water scarcity and suggest a solution plan. In this way, the problem solving method can be adopted effectively.

Seminar method: It is possible to have a comprehensive discussion on various socio-cultural issues through seminar teaching method. Through this teaching method, it is possible to conduct seminars on various cultural diversity and cultural features. This helps in developing a sense of belonging among the students in different cultures. Seminar teaching method is very effective in multicultural education as it focuses on expert opinion on a social issue as well as group discussion.

Conclusion

Multicultural education is the need of the hour. In a secular nation like India, multicultural curriculum is much needed in terms of cultural mutual respect, goodwill, preservation, nurture and transition of culture. Multicultural curriculum, multicultural learning teaching methods, equality in classroom teaching, school democratic environment, equality of opportunity, creation of mutual cultural tolerance are essential for the future education system and certainly for the development of the country.

References

- [1] Shankar Dasharath Dunghav, Educational Resurgence, "Global Emerging Trends in Transformation of Education", Journal Volume-3, Special Issue June, 2021 ISSN 2581-9100
- [2] Grant, N. (1997). Some Problems of Identity and Education: A comparative examination of multicultural education. *Comparative Education*, 33(1), 9–28. doi:10.1080/03050069728613.
- [3] <https://www.accreditedschoolsonline.org/resources/student-diversity-multicultural/>
- [4] <https://web.uri.edu/teach/multicultural/>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

NEEDS AND IMPORTANCE OF MULTICULTURALISM IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. Multicultural education also assumes that the ways in which students learn and think are deeply influenced by their cultural identity and heritage, and that to teach culturally diverse students effectively requires educational approaches that value and recognize their cultural backgrounds. In this paper present on needs and importance of multiculturalism and multicultural education aims to improve the learning and success of all students and ways of representative play outs the schools.

Introduction

Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. At the classroom level, for example, teachers may modify or incorporate lessons to reflect the cultural diversity of the students in a particular class. In many cases, “culture” is defined in the broadest possible sense, encompassing race, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, and “exceptionality” a term applied to students with specialized needs or disabilities. Generally speaking, multicultural education is predicated on the principle of educational equity for all students, regardless of culture, and it strives to remove barriers to educational opportunities and success for students from different cultural backgrounds. In practice, educators may modify or eliminate educational policies, programs, materials, lessons, and instructional practices that are either discriminatory toward or insufficiently inclusive of diverse cultural perspectives. Multicultural education also assumes that the ways in which students learn and think are deeply influenced by their cultural identity and heritage, and that to teach culturally diverse students effectively requires educational approaches that value and recognize their cultural backgrounds. In this way, multicultural education aims to improve the learning and success of all students, particularly students from cultural groups that have been historically underrepresented or that suffer from lower educational achievement and attainment.

Needs and Importance of Multiculturalism in Education

To identifications of the culture: Multicultural education not only enables students to get acquainted with different cultures but also inculcates in students an attitude of respect for the culture of others besides their own culture, sensitivity and empathy towards the culture of others.

To create cultural Integration: It is possible to create cultural integration among students through multicultural education. Also cultural integration has a positive effect on the integrity of the whole country. The Importance of Cultural Integration in Society Consequences and its Benefits Helps to get education in this regard, multicultural education enhances cultural integration and helps in fostering a sense of belonging to different cultures in the society.

To develop responsible citizenship: Intelligent and responsible citizens are the wealth of the country. The progress of any country depends on the development of its society. In such a situation, the process of developing responsible citizenship through multicultural education is very fast. That is why multicultural education is sorely needed to develop competent citizens.

To create broad positive social approaches: Multicultural education is desperately needed to create a broad positive social outlook. Multicultural education is of paramount importance in the development of responsible citizenship through education. For social development is not possible without inculcating social awareness, it is possible to inculcate a comprehensive positive social attitude in students through multicultural education. In fact, it takes time.

To Cultivate global spirit: It is the duty of education to create a global feeling in the students, for which it is easy to make the students fit for the global competition through cultural education. In today's 21st century era of competition, multicultural education will make it possible for students to integrate into a global culture.

To create unity through diversity: India is a culturally diverse country. In such a scenario, multicultural education is important to inculcate in the students the feeling that we are all Indians without cultural differences in order to realize the principle of secularism.

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Way of representative Multicultural Education: The following are a few representative ways in which multicultural education may play out in schools:

Learning Content

Texts and learning materials may include multiple cultural perspectives and references. For example a lesson on Indian Culture might address different cultural perspectives, such as those of the North, South, West and East Indian cultures.

Student Cultures

Teachers and other educators may learn about the cultural backgrounds of students in a school, and then intentionally incorporate learning experiences and content relevant to their personal cultural perspectives and heritage. Students may also be encouraged to learn about the cultural backgrounds of other students in a class, and students from different cultures may be given opportunities to discuss and share their cultural experiences.

Critical Analysis

Educators may intentionally scrutinize learning materials to identify potentially prejudicial or biased material. Both educators and students might analyze their own cultural assumptions, and then discuss how learning materials, teaching practices, or schools policies reflect cultural bias, and how they could be changed to eliminate bias.

Resource Allocation

Multicultural education is generally predicated on the principle of equity that the allocation and distribution of educational resources, programs, and learning experiences should be based on need and fairness, rather than strict equality. For example, students who are not proficient in the English language may learn in bilingual settings and read bilingual texts, and they may receive comparatively more instructional support than their English-speaking peers so that they do not fall behind academically or drop out of school due to language limitations.

Conclusion

Multicultural education is the need of the hour. In a secular nation like India, multicultural curriculum is much needed in terms of cultural mutual respect, goodwill, preservation, nurture and transition of culture. Multicultural curriculum and ways to representative in play outs in schools are very essential in process to develop multicultural education among students.

References

- [1] Annamalai, E. (2001). *Managing multilingualism in India: political and linguistic manifestations*, New Delhi. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [2] Banks, J. A. (2008). *An introduction to multicultural education* Boston, MA: Pearson/Allyn and Bacon.
- [3] Banks, J. A., & Banks, C. A. M. (2010). *Multicultural education: issues and perspectives* (7th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley
- [4] <https://www.accreditedschoolsonline.org/resources/student-diversity-multicultural/>
- [5] <https://web.uri.edu/teach/multicultural/>
- [6] <https://idronline.org/nep-2020>
- [7] <https://www.edglossary.org/multiculturaleducation>

CURRICULUM IN OUTCOME-BASED EDUCATION

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Abstract

The “Outcome-Based Education” (OBE) model is being adopted at a fast pace in education institutions. It's considered an enormous breakthrough to enhance education across the world. Outcome-based education (OBE) may be a student-centered instruction model that focuses on measuring student performance through outcomes. Outcomes include knowledge, skills, and attitudes. There's a hidden contradiction within the projection and implementation of the OBE. One results in Multidisciplinary and therefore the other results in OBE. At first, we expect freedom and in other structured progress is predicted. One results in democratic knowledge and therefore the other results in capitalist knowledge management. Our education is sort of a lady with over ornaments who is unable to steer simply because of the load she carries of the ornaments. Technology silences the mind and not questioning a mind and thus this information society or knowledge society is ignorant and this may come whenever and wherever we mention mass education and not class education. This paper discusses the necessity and importance of curriculum formation and within the Outcome Based education –OBE.

Keywords: *Education, Curriculum, Outcome Based Education.*

Outcome-Based Education

There is a difference between Output and Outcome. The first is the product or service of any process. It is what we create, develop or deliver. In the education System Certificates or degrees is the output. It measures the quantity of knowledge of the students. While the Outcome is the result of performance. It is the quality of output. Competencies, Ability, Skills, Attitude, Performance, etc.

Curriculum

The term curriculum means many things to many people. Any decide to define the concept within the context isn't aimed toward seeking the consensus of interpretation but rather an understanding of the meaning attached to the concept. Curriculum refers to planned learning experiences that the tutorial institution intends to provide for its learners. Despite the shortage of agreement on the meaning of the term, there seems to be a consensus that educational institutions, as institutions charged with the all-important societal function of teaching citizens, have the only claim to the curriculum. Furthermore, most agree that within the education of all forms, there is no such thing as being neutral. Some authors believe that education should be directed towards helping learners become intelligent and important citizens during a democratic society, yet for a few, education may be a political act that ‘demands from educators that they take it on as a political act which they consistently live their progressive and democratic or authoritarian and reactionary past or also their spontaneous, uncritical choice, that they define themselves by being democratic or authoritarian’. Put simply, either the learners got to be taught to suit as a cog into the prevailing social machinery, or to find out to acknowledge their responsibility. For the transformation of the social, political, and economic world during which they live.

Curriculum in OBE

Curriculum making is a dynamic process, not a one-time event. Instructors' wisdom, quality, creativeness and interest are the foundation to making a curriculum. There is a difference between syllabus and Curriculum. Syllabus: A concise statement of facts or table of the heads of a course or subjects of a series of lectures. Curriculum: A set of guidelines to achieve the academic objectives. The curriculum is a serious exercise that needs to be taken seriously. To define the word curriculum is not an easy matter. In the classical period of Greek civilization, Curriculum has been described what has been taught during the specific time slot. In 1970 Pinar (1974) defined Curriculum as lived experience.

The Curriculum Has To Consider 3 Levels

The planned Curriculum is all about the important goals and objectives, what knowledge is most worthy. The Planned Curriculum according to Cambell is the Legitimation of Standardized guidelines. It has a Curricular authority.

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The Enacted Curriculum deals with how it is to be implemented and evaluated. The teacher has to judge the Pedagogical Knowledge and to be translated in use. Curriculum enactment is a plan to be implemented.

Experience Curriculum refers to what happens in the class which is the live wire of educational experience, which is called as lived experience. This lived experience is individual, ongoing, and unpredictable but 21st-century information Society does not limit itself to the class—restricted to Community but it is in individual control and is more powerful. Certain definitions do provide insights about common emphasis and characteristics within the general idea of curriculum. Over and above following three levels can also be consider from the view point of implementation

Five Major Principles about Curriculum in Outcome Based Education

Five major principles about curriculum presented by

- 1) The concern with the experiences of learners
- 2) Making decisions about content and process
- 3) Making decisions about a variety of issues and topics
- 4) Involving many groups
- 5) Decision making at may levels

Concept of the Curriculum

The concept of the curriculum by **Walker** emphasized three important aspects.

- 1) Content
- 2) Purpose
- 3) Organization

The following table represents the curriculum for the new millennium which was presented by Longstreet and Shane in the year.

Social Oriented Curriculum	Schooling is to serve Society
Students centred Curriculum	Student a crucial source of all curriculum
Knowledge centred Curriculum	Knowledge is the hear of curriculum
Eclectic Curriculum	Totality is the bear of curriculum

Eisner and Vance have given the following important elements of the curriculum which were modified and revised the original Concept of 1974 in 1986 they deleted self actualization orientation and added personal success and personal commitment

- 1) Conflicting conceptions of curriculum
- 2) A cognitive process of orientation
- 3) Technological orientation
- 4) Self actualization orientation
- 5) Social re-constructionist orientation
- 6) Academic re-constructionist orientation

Conclusion

This paper provides an overview of the key importance of Outcomes-Based Education and Curriculum in various contexts. The level of educator's understating of OBE is still very low. For successful implementation of OBE, the educators should understand the OBE system. All of sudden the traditional approaches should not be thrown away, but should be used as a means towards implementing OBE. Affiliating universities should frame the curriculum.

Reference:

- [1] Davis, M. H. (2003). Outcome-based education. Journal of veterinary medical education, 30(3), 258-263
- [2] Eisner, E. (2002). The arts and the creation of mind. New Haven, CT: Yale University

EVALUATION IN OUTCOME-BASED EDUCATION

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Abstract

Outcome-based education is criticized for reducing education, teaching, and learning to kinds of human engineering and quasi-scientific planning procedures geared toward instrumental means and specified ends. Stating outcomes as a comprehensive kind of intellectual scaffolding limits inquiry and speculation and provides institutions and curriculum framers unwarranted authority over knowledge and understanding. Transitional outcome-based education lies within the twilight zone between traditional material curriculum structures and planning processes and thus the future-role priorities inherent in transformational OBE. Districts undergo incorporation, integration, and redefinition stages in implementing transitional OBE. This paper discusses the process of evaluation in outcome based education in teaching learning process.

What is OBE?

The “Outcome-Based Education” (OBE) model is being adopted at a fast pace in education institutions. it's considered an enormous breakthrough to enhance education across the world . Outcome-based education (OBE) may be a student-centered instruction model that focuses on measuring student performance through outcomes. Outcomes include knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Its focus remains on the evaluation of outcomes of the program by stating the knowledge, skill and behavior a graduate is predicted to realize upon completion of a program and after 4 – 5 years of graduation. within the OBE model, the required knowledge and skillsets for a selected engineering degree are predetermined and thus the scholars are evaluated for all the required parameters (Outcomes) during the course of the program.

Why do institutions got to follow OBE?

There is a seamless and cross-institutional approach to market OBE. for instance , the induction of India within the Washington Accord in 2014 with the permanent signatory status of The National Board of Accreditation (NBA) is taken into account an enormous breakthrough for the higher-education system in India. It means an Engineering graduate from India are often employed in anybody of the other countries who has signed the accord (Know more about the Washington accord here). For Indian Engineering Institutions to urge accredited by NBA according to the pacts of the accord, engineering institutions must follow the result Based Education (OBE) model. So, for an Engineering Institution to be accredited by NBA it should compulsorily follow the OBE model.

How is it Measured?

The OBE model measures the progress of the graduate in three parameters, which are

- 1) Program Educational Objectives (PEO)
- 2) Program Outcomes (PO)
- 3) Course Outcomes (CO)

Program Educational Objectives (PEO) are broad statements that describe the career and professional accomplishments that the program is preparing the graduates to understand . PEO's are measured 4-5 years after graduation. Program outcomes are narrower statements that describe what students are expected to know and be able to treat at the time of graduation. Course outcomes are the measurable parameters that evaluates each students performance for each course that the scholar undertakes in every semester.

Methods of Assessment

Traditional Assessment as per established Taxonomies:

The method of assessment of the candidates during the program is left for the institution to form a choice . the varied assessment tools for measuring Course Outcomes include Mid -Semester and End Semester Examinations, Tutorials, Assignments, Project work, Labs, Presentations, Employer/Alumni Feedback, etc.. These course outcomes are mapped to Graduate attributes and Program outcomes supported

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relevance. This evaluation pattern helps Institutions to measure the Program Outcome. The Program Educational Objective is measure through Employer satisfaction survey (Yearly), Alumni survey (Yearly), Placement records, and better education records.

Formative Assessment

- 1) To monitor student learning and to supply ongoing feedback which will be employed by instructors to enhance their teaching and by students to enhance their learning.
- 2) Help students identify their strengths and weaknesses and target areas that require work
- 3) Help faculty recognize where students are struggling and address problems immediately
- 4) Examples of formative assessments include asking students to:
- 5) Submit one or two sentences about a piece of writing or lecture during a discussion forum
- 6) Complete a little quiz
- 7) Upload/submit a visible depiction of an idea

Summative Assessment

- 1) To evaluate student learning at the top of an instructional unit by comparing it against a typical or benchmark.
- 2) Often high stakes, which suggests that they need a part value and a big impact on the course grade.
- 3) Examples of summative assessments include:
- 4) Exams
- 5) Projects and
- 6) Papers

Information from summative assessments are often used formatively when students or faculty use it to guide their efforts and activities in subsequent courses. In Bloom's Taxonomy, the evaluation level is where students make judgments about the worth of ideas, items, materials, and more. Evaluation is that the final level of Bloom's taxonomy pyramid. it's at this level, where students are expected to usher in all they need learned to form informed and sound evaluations of fabric. Key Words for the Evaluation Category are-evaluate, appraise, conclude, criticize, critique Particular success lies within the effective adoption and stringent accreditation process to make sure the standard of education is maintained. Outcome-based education (OBE) means focusing and organizing everything in a tutorial system around what's essential for all students to be able to do successfully at the highest of their learning experiences. Despite the popularity of outcome-based education, research documenting its effects is rare. As an umbrella concept embracing various reform efforts.

Challenges

- 1) Meaning of the term "outcome-based education" and the way they're derived.
- 2) Current interest in OBE to global socio-economic changes.
- 3) The way to choose classroom reform,
- 4) The way to choose program alignment,
- 5) The way to create external accountability,
- 6) The way to achieve system transformation,
- 7) The way to sustain it over time.

The Curriculum in CBCS (choice-based credit system)

Prime concern about the CBCS is why we'd like it during a country like India where at every 100 km culture, understanding and problems are different. Recently many stakeholders in India protested for implementing CBCS and still, there's controversy regarding the implementation of CBCS at education institutions. However, we'd like CBCS because we'd like to get rid of the singular structure of data, which means Knowledge isn't a monolithic structure. The monolithic structure has damaged the potentiality of data. it's damaged the thread of knowing or potentiality to think, which is damaging the spirit of Education because education demands knowledge in totality, therefore, we do require CBCS (choice-based credit system). it's also useful for opening the multidimensional way of thinking, not imposed but entertained by the liberty to settle on. So virtue of CBCS is freedom of choice. to make Potentiality to think differently give birth to innovative learning. So CBCS provides a backbone for Creativity. It provides space for the liberty to think differently. Self-reflexivity and freedom to think are the essential stone on which this structure of CBCS

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is to be created and therefore the entire gamut of learning should be build and Carved. But the way to make it possible. How the spirit of CBCS to be translated and exhibited is a tutorial exercise, which is obligatory for education to think and execute. this will be done by creating the structure of curriculum befitting to the spirit of upper education.

Conclusion

This paper provides an overview of the key importance and process of Evaluation in Outcomes-Based Education. The level of educator's understating of OBE is still very low. For successful implementation of OBE, the educators should understand the OBE system. All of sudden the traditional approaches should not be thrown away, but should be used as a means towards implementing OBE and use in evaluation of students achievement.

Reference

- [1] Acharya, C.. Outcome-based education (OBE): A new paradigm for learning. Centre for Development of Teaching and Learning (Singapore), 2003.
- [2] International Engineering Alliance, 25 Years of the Washington Accord
- [3] Bouslama, F., Lansari, A., Al-Rawi, A., & Abonamah, A. A. A novel outcome-based educational model and its effect on student learning, curriculum development, and assessment. *Journal of Information Technology Education*, 2003.
- [4] Bloom, B. S. (1956). *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, Handbook I: The Cognitive Domain*. New York: David McKay Co Inc.
- [5] Anderson, L. W., and Krathwohl, D. R. (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing, Abridged Edition*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.

INFLUENCE OF METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS ON SCIENTIFIC LITERACY AND GOAL ORIENTATION OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Metacognition is “knowledge concerning one’s cognitive processes and regulation of these cognitive activities in the learning process”. Goal Orientation refers to the relevant purposes or aims that individuals strive for in achievement settings, and these different purposes or aims are posited to lead to differential performance outcomes. Scientific literacy is the “ability of students to use their scientific knowledge and skills in different areas and different life situations. The paper intends to find out the influence of metacognition on scientific literacy and goal orientation of higher secondary school students. The investigator used the normative survey method for the present study. A sample of 225 higher secondary students was selected. The investigator used Metacognitive Awareness Scale, Scientific Literacy Scale, and Goal Orientation Scale was used to collect the data. Descriptive statistics, coefficient of correlation, and regression were used for interpreting the data. The investigator found that the level of metacognition, scientific literacy, and goal orientation of higher secondary school students is moderate. The investigator analysed a high positive correlation between metacognition and scientific literacy, metacognition and goal orientation and scientific literacy and goal orientation among higher secondary school students. The investigator concluded that Metacognition is a significant predictor of scientific literacy also goal orientation of higher secondary school students.

Keywords: *Metacognition, Scientific literacy, Goal orientation, Higher Secondary*

Introduction

Education is a complex system embedded with the physical, psychological and sociological context of teaching-learning, which strengthens the inner capacities of children through the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes. One of the significant aims of education is bringing quality in different spheres like content, process and environments, which ultimately produce diverse outcomes favourable for self and society. Today, the progress index of humanity is reflected by developments and advancements in science and technology. Education provides a proper link between scientific inventions and their dissemination (M karada, 2018). The quality of education has been positively changed by the rapid development of science Darling Hammond et al. 2019. This quality of education further paved the way to transition from teacher-centred to student-centred education, changing the conventional understanding of education (Kasim and Aini, 2012). The objective of education in the 21st century aims not only to provide students with a huge amount of knowledge and information but also to prepare students to become effective and independent learners, who have self-regulatory skills and can achieve academic success as long as life success.

The concept of Metacognition encounters numerous definitions from a wide array of research. The most common description for metacognition is “knowledge concerning one’s cognitive processes and regulation of these cognitive activities in the learning process” (Flavell, 1979 & Brown, 1987). Here, “Meta” refers to “a change of position, a sense of going beyond the ordinary level” or “to a second order or higher level thinking”, and “cognition” refers to the process of knowing or thinking. Baker and Brown (1984) defined metacognitive knowledge by explaining the difference between static and strategic knowledge. Pintrich (2002) defined “students becoming more knowledgeable of and responsible for their cognition and thinking”. The term metacognition emerged from the early work of Flavell (1979), who referred to it as knowledge concerning one’s cognitive processes and products or anything related to them (Dutke, Barenberg & Leopold 2010; Phelps, Ellis & Hase, 2001). Wolters (2003) identified self-regulated learners as “the persons with the cognitive, metacognitive abilities as well as motivational beliefs required to understand, monitor, and direct their own learning”. College-aged students can take advantage of using strategies under metacognition strategies.

Moreover, students can understand metacognitive skills to enhance their learning (Fisher et al., 2015; Barenberg and Dutke, 2019). Pintrich (2002) argues that teachers must teach metacognitive knowledge comprehensively. Furthermore, the crucial components of student-centred education are among the study procedures, where students use metacognitive awareness, regulate their own study procedures, and possess

motivation. Metacognitive awareness, metacognitive experiences, metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive beliefs, metacognitive skills, high-level skills, and upper memory are some terms associated with metacognition (Veenman et al., 2006; Yeşilyurt, 2013).

Goal Orientation emerged as a result of socio - cognitive representations of motivation. For the past two decades, it has been one of the major concerns of many educational researchers (Elliot & McGregor, 2001; Elliot & Murayama, 2008; Pintrich, 2000). According to Dweck (1989), whenever students are in a learning environment, they are assumed to have specific goals in learning which are referred to as achievement goals. The two main types of goals are mastery and achievement (Dweck and Leggett, 1988). The students with mastery goal orientation concentrate on learning and mastering the subject content. Those who have dominant mastery goals have characteristics of accepting challenging tasks and striving under difficult conditions. These people have a solution-oriented approach and respond to a failure to solve the problem, which in turn positively impacts performance with improvement (Elliot & Dweck, 1988). On the other side, the performance goals motivate the students to get better scores to avoid incompatibility (Dweck & Leggett, 1988). People who possess performance goals tend to exhibit skill and avoid the impression of a lack of competency. (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; Elliot & Dweck, 1988). Goal Orientation refers to the relevant purposes or aims that individuals strive for in achievement settings, and these different purposes or aims are posited to lead to differential performance outcomes (Elliot, Shell, Henry & Maier, 2005). Goal Orientation refers to the relevant purposes or aims that individuals strive for in achievement settings, and these different purposes or aims are posited to lead to differential performance outcomes (Elliot, Shell, Henry & Maier, 2005).

Over the last two decades, "scientific literacy" has become a famous educational slogan and a significant objective for science education in many nations (Millar, 2006). PISA (2006) defines scientific literacy as the "ability of students to use their scientific knowledge and skills in different areas and life situations". Hazen & Trefil (1991) scientific literacy as "the knowledge you need to understand public issues. It is a mix of facts, vocabulary, concepts, history, and philosophy" Defined at the simplest level "scientific literacy" is just another name for "what the general public ought to know about Science" (Durant, 1993). According to Bybee (1997), "The phrase scientific literacy for all learners expresses the major goal of Science education to attain society's aspirations and advance individual development within the context of Science and technology". Roberts (1983) echoed this view "scientific literacy has had so many interpretations that it now means virtually everything to do with Science education" and now it has "become an umbrella concept to signify comprehensiveness in the purposes of Science teaching in the schools". Understanding the scientific method may be even more crucial (Maienschein, 1999).

The relationship between metacognition and scientific literacy is complex and multi-faceted. Metacognition, or the ability to think about thinking, can be a powerful tool for enhancing scientific literacy. Metacognition facilitates the development of self-regulation skills that can be applied to scientific inquiry and problem-solving. Metacognition and goal orientation are closely related. Goal orientation is an individual's attitude toward achievement and learning, and metacognition is an individual's awareness and control over their own cognition. People with a vital goal orientation tend to be more aware of their own learning processes and engage in more metacognitive activities. Studies have shown that students with higher goal orientations tend to use more metacognitive strategies and perform better on academic tasks. In other words, metacognition and goal orientation are intertwined and can be used in tandem to improve academic performance.

Metacognition is a powerful tool to help students become more scientifically literate and goal-oriented. Research has found that metacognitive strategies can help students better understand scientific concepts, improve their ability to think critically, and increase their motivation to achieve their goals by encouraging students to reflect on their knowledge and understanding of scientific concepts.

Need and Significance of the Study

A novice learner avoids rote learning of concepts and uses inquiry-based approaches from simple cognitive tasks to complex cognitive problems. Higher-order mental processes such as reasoning, problem-solving, and reflective thinking emerged from science classes and paves the way to develop metacognitive abilities among learners. The term metacognition is quite difficult as it is thinking beyond thinking, yet all people engage in metacognitive activities, becoming an inseparable part of their everyday life. Costa and Kallick (2001) identified the significant role of metacognition in education because it helps the learner develop a plan and monitor and evaluate its effectiveness. That means metacognition helps the learner be more involved in the learning process. Metacognition significantly enhances scientific skills like problem-solving at the elementary and college level (Swanson, 1990). Furthermore, metacognition creates successful learners with self-regulated learning abilities,

making them active and constructive participants.

Ata et al. (2019) Examined nursing students' metacognitive thinking and goal orientation as predictors of academic motivation at the Faculty of Nursing, Zagazig University, Egypt. Findings revealed that Nursing students' metacognitive thinking and goal orientation were significant predictors of academic motivation. Cai Y et al. (2019) examined how future goals, metacognitive strategies, and achievement dynamically influence each other across time. Results of the study indicated that multi-level cross-lagged structural equation modelling showed that: (1) intrinsic goals are adaptive because they are associated with the lower pursuit of extrinsic goals and higher levels of achievement; (2) the use of meta-cognitive learning strategies is associated with an increase in intrinsic goal pursuit; and (3) higher levels of achievement drive the subsequent use of metacognitive strategies. Theoretical and practical implications are discussed. Gul A and Shehzad S (2012) find the relationship between metacognition, goal orientation and academic achievement among graduates of public and private universities. The results showed a moderate relationship between metacognition and goal orientation and academic achievement, but a weak relationship was found between metacognition and achievement.

Al-Harthy and Was (2012) identified the relationship between Goals, self-efficacy and Metacognitive self-regulation and examined the joint contribution of each variable on students' scores in 12 exams. Results revealed that self-efficacy, self-regulation, task value and elaboration showed a significant positive correlation with the total score. Edwards (2010) examined the effect of Achievement Goal Orientation on attention, learning and Metacognitive Awareness. Significant results of the study indicated that achievement goals and learning partially mediated attention.

Metacognition is the ability to think about one's thinking. It involves the understanding and active monitoring of one's own thinking processes and recognizing their own strengths and weaknesses. By developing metacognitive skills, higher secondary school students can become more aware of their learning and be better equipped to understand and effectively use the resources and strategies they need to succeed in their scientific studies. Metacognition can also help students become more goal-oriented, allowing them to focus on the task at hand and set goals for themselves. By understanding the science concepts more deeply, students can build an understanding of the scientific process, which in turn can lead to increased goal orientation and scientific literacy.

For the present study, Metacognition is defined as a learner's awareness/self-assessment about how they prepare and plan for learning, select and use various learning strategies, and monitor and evaluate the strategy used for learning. Reviewing various research works, the investigator found that metacognition, scientific literacy and goal orientation are more relevant and vital in the present scenario. Hence the present study is entitled "INFLUENCE OF METACOGNITION ON SCIENTIFIC LITERACY AND GOAL ORIENTATION OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS."

Hypotheses Formulated for the Study

- 1) The level of Metacognition of higher secondary school students is moderate.
- 2) The level of Scientific Literacy of higher secondary school students is moderate.
- 3) The level of Goal Orientation of higher secondary school students is moderate.
- 4) There will be significant relationship between Metacognition and Scientific Literacy of higher secondary school students
- 5) There will be significant relationship between Metacognition and Goal Orientation of higher secondary school students
- 6) There will be significant relationship between Scientific Literacy and Goal Orientation of higher secondary school students
- 7) Metacognition is a significant predictor of Scientific Literacy of higher secondary school students.
- 8) Metacognition is a significant predictor of Goal Orientation of higher secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the level of Metacognition among higher secondary school students.
- 2) To find out the level of Scientific Literacy among higher secondary school students
- 3) To find out the level of Goal Orientation among higher secondary school students.
- 4) To find out the relationship between Metacognition and Scientific Literacy among higher secondary school students.
- 5) To find out the relationship between Metacognition and Goal Orientation among higher secondary school students.
- 6) To find out the relationship between Scientific Literacy and Goal Orientation among higher secondary

school students.

- 7) To find out the predictability of Metacognition on Scientific Literacy of higher secondary school students.
- 8) To find out the predictability of Metacognition on Goal orientation of higher secondary school students.

Methodology in Brief

The Investigator adopted a normative survey method for the study. The population of the study includes all the higher secondary school students in Kerala. A sample of 225 higher secondary school students from the Thiruvananthapuram district was selected for the present study. The cluster sampling technique was employed for the present study. Tools used for the present study were the Metacognitive Awareness Scale, Scientific Literacy Scale and Goal Orientation Scale. Metacognitive awareness Scale with selected components of knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition and scientific literacy scale with components of attitudinal, behavioural domain, content knowledge, and scientific reasoning and Goal Orientation Scale with selected components of Mastery Goal Orientation, Performance-Approach Goal Orientation and PerformanceAvoidance Goal Orientation dimensions was used for collecting data. The data collected were analysed using Descriptive Statistics, t-test, and Karl Pearson product-moment correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Analysis of the Level of Metacognition of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 1 Classification of higher secondary school students based on their level of metacognition

Level	N	Percentage
High	52	23
Moderate	120	54
Low	53	24

Table 1 depicts that 23% of higher secondary school students have a high level of metacognition, 54 % of higher secondary school students have a moderate level of metacognition, and 24% of higher secondary school students have a low level of metacognition. Hence, the investigator concluded that the metacognition of higher secondary school students is moderate.

Figure 1 Showing the level of metacognition of higher secondary school students

Analysis of the Level of Scientific Literacy of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 2 Classification of higher secondary school students based on their level of scientific literacy

Level	N	Percentage
High	45	20
Moderate	104	46
Low	76	34

Figure 2 Showing the level of scientific literacy of higher secondary school students

Table 2 depicts that 20% of higher secondary school students have high scientific literacy, 46% of higher secondary school students have moderate scientific literacy, and 34% of higher secondary school students have low scientific literacy. Hence, the investigator concluded that the scientific literacy of higher secondary school students is moderate

Analysis of the Level of Goal Orientation of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 3 Classification of higher secondary school students based on their level of goal orientation

Level	N	Percentage
High	60	26
Moderate	123	55
Low	42	19

Figure 3 Showing the level of goal orientation of higher secondary school students

Table 3 depicts that 20% of higher secondary school students have high goal orientation, 55% of higher secondary school students have moderate goal orientation, and 19% of higher secondary school students have low goal orientation. Hence, the investigator concluded that the goal orientation of higher secondary school students is moderate.

Analysis of Relationship Between Metacognition and Scientific Literacy of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 4 Shows the relationship between metacognition and scientific literacy of higher secondary school students

Variables	N	Co-efficient of correlation (r)	t	level of significance	SEr	95% CI	
Metacognition						Lower	Upper
Goal Orientation	0.98	82.15	0.01	1.85	1.31	1.37	0.98

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From table 4, the investigator used Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation (r) to study the intensity of the relationship between metacognition and scientific literacy of higher secondary school students. The obtained value of r is .98, the calculated $r = .98$, and is significant at the 0.05 level. ($r = .98$; $p < 0.05$). Investigator concluded a high positive correlation between metacognition and scientific literacy of higher secondary school students.

Analysis of Relationship Between Metacognition and Goal Orientation of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 5 Shows the relationship between metacognition and goal orientation of higher secondary school students

Variables	N	Co-efficient of correlation (r)	t	level of significance	SEr	95% CI	
Metacognition						Lower	Upper
Goal Orientation	225	0.90	31.09	0.05	7.05	1.81	2.05

From table 5, the investigator used Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation (r) to study the intensity of the relationship between metacognition and goal orientation of higher secondary school students. The obtained value of r is 0.90, the calculated $r = 0.90$, and is significant at the 0.05 level. ($r = .432$; $p < 0.05$). Investigator concluded a high positive correlation between metacognition and goal orientation of higher secondary school students.

Analysis of Relationship Between Scientific Literacy and Goal Orientation of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 6 Shows the relationship between scientific literacy and goal orientation of higher secondary school students

Variables	N	Co-efficient of correlation (r)	t	level of significance	SEr	95% CI	
Metacognition						Lower	Upper
Goal Orientation	225	0.908	32.42	0.01	4.33	0.543	0.613

From table 6, the investigator used Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation (r) to study the intensity of the relationship between scientific literacy and the goal orientation of higher secondary school students. The calculated $r = 0.908$, the calculated $r = 0.908$, and is significant at the 0.05 level. ($r = 0.908$; $p < 0.05$). The investigator concluded a high positive correlation between scientific literacy and the goal orientation of higher secondary school students.

Find out the Predictability of Metacognition on Scientific Literacy of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 7.1 Model summary of metacognition and scientific literacy
Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.984	0.968	0.968	8.21923

- 1) Predictors: (Constant), Metacognition
- 2) Dependent Variable: Scientific literacy

Table 7.2 ANOVA table for metacognition and scientific literacy ANOVA

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23181.238	1	23181.238	6.750E3	.000a
	Residual	765.891	223	3.434		
	Total	23947.129	224			

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Table-7.3 Regression table for metacognition and scientific literacy Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(C(constant))	-50.508	2.091		-24.161	0.01
	Metacognition	1.344	0.016	0.984	82.156	0.01

Dependent Variable: Scientific literacy. From the above tables-7.1, 7.2, 7.3, it is significant ($F_{(67.5)} = 62.102$, $p > 0.01$, $R^2 = .968$). Further from the standardized beta coefficients examination, the study found that metacognition is a significant predictor of scientific literacy ($\beta = .984$, $p > 0.01$). At the same time, it can be interpreted as 19.1% of the variance in scientific literacy can be explained by the metacognition of higher secondary school students. Thus, the regression equation calculated from the above result is $Y = 13.44X + 60.50$. Therefore, scientific literacy = $.801$ (metacognition) + 64.641

To Find Out the Predictability of Metacognition on Goal Orientation of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 8.1 Model summary of metacognition and goal orientation
Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.901	.813	0.812	7.05088

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Metacognition
b. Dependent Variable: Goal orientation

Table 8.2 ANOVA table for metacognition and goal orientation
ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	48069.372	1	48069.372	966.901	0.01
	Residual	11086423	223	49.715		
	Total	59155	224			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Metacognition
b. Dependent Variable: Goal orientation

Table-8.3 Regression table for Metacognition and Goal orientation Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-166.169	7.954		2.0.892	0.05

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	Metacognition	1.936	.062	0.901	31.095	0.01
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a. Dependent Variable: Goal orientation

F From the above tables-8.1, 8.2, 8.3, it is significant ($F_{(96.69)} = 59.152$ $p < 0.01$, $R^2 = .813$). Further from the standardized beta coefficients examination, the study found that metacognition is a significant predictor of goal orientation ($\beta = .901$, $p < 0.01$). At the same time, it can be interpreted as 18.3% of the variance in goal orientation can be explained by the metacognition of higher secondary school students. Thus, the regression equation calculated from the above result is $Y = 1.93 + 16.61$.

Therefore, goal orientation = 0.661 (Metacognition) + 16.272

Findings of the Study

The investigator found that the level of metacognition, scientific literacy, and goal orientation of higher secondary school students is moderate. The investigator analysed that there is a high positive correlation between metacognition and scientific literacy, metacognition and goal orientation also scientific literacy and goal orientation among higher secondary school students. The investigator concluded that Metacognition is a significant predictor of scientific literacy also goal orientation of higher secondary school students.

Educational Implications

Metacognition has important implications for educational contexts. It can help students develop self-regulation and self-monitoring skills, which allow them to become more independent and resourceful learners. Metacognition can also help students develop better problem-solving skills as they become more aware of their own cognitive processes and are better able to identify potential strategies for solving a task. Metacognition can help students become more organized and efficient in their approach to learning and support their ability to set goals and plan their learning process. Goal orientation will help the teachers to get motivated by a clear vision, mission, goal or aspiration. Goal Setting Theory states that students with a specific goals will do better than students with unspecified goal. Scientific literacy also encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity, which are essential skills for success in any field. Scientific literacy also encourages students to think more critically about the world and to challenge accepted beliefs. Scientific literacy brings skills for achieving knowledge rather than teaching the existing knowledge to the students. science literacy is critical because it provides a context for addressing societal problems. A science-literate person can effectively cope with many problems and make intelligent decisions that will affect the quality of their life and those of their children.

References

- [1] Akın, A. (2012). Achievement Goal Orientations and Age. *TOJCE: The Online Journal of Counselling and Education*, 1, 77-81.
- [2] Akin, A., Abaci, R., & Cetin, B. (2007). The Validity and Reliability of the Turkish Version of the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 7(2), 671-678.
- [3] Alci, B., & Karatas, H. (2011). Teacher candidates' metacognitive awareness according to their domains and sex. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Thought*, 1(6), 255-263.
- [4] Asim T., Aini T.S. Doctoral dissertation, Auckland University of Technology; 2012. Teaching and Learning Experiences in Malaysian Higher Education: a Case Study of a Teacher Education Programme.

BLENDING LEARNING IN ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE: TOWARDS ACHIEVING HOLISTIC OUTCOME

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Abstract

Knowledge acquisition along with development of life skills constitute the holistic outcome of education in 21st century. The overall development of a learner to become an active participant of society is the focus of new educational policy. NEP 2020 states that holistic development of each student in both academic and non-academic sphere should be facilitated by recognising, identifying and fostering the unique capabilities of each student. This can be done when there will be effective communication between the teachers and learners. Learning of language is essential to channel our thoughts and ideas to others and comprehend the world around us. With the rapid growth of information and technology educational endeavour is inclining towards using more of ICT in teaching and learning process. Blended learning is such an example of hybrid learning which includes both the traditional as well as online modes. It has many advantages that push the boundaries of traditional classroom practises and lead to better results for students. The use of blended learning has the potential to help students learn English as a second language and give them more chances to practise the English language on their own time. This paper discusses how blended learning in English as second language is helpful towards achieving holistic outcomes for students.

Keywords: Blended Learning, ESL, Holistic Outcome.

Introduction

“By education, I mean an all-round drawing of the best in child and man in body, mind and spirit.”

-M.K. Gandhi

Education either in the formal or informal structure do have specific goals in terms of behavioural change or achieving certain skills for the better future of every learner. To bring forth the holistic development of an individual physical, mental and social wellbeing must be taken into account. The teaching learning process of nowadays must look into the needs of learners pertaining to contemporary society. In the world of advanced technology education must not lag behind in terms of its implications. Efforts must be channelized towards using modern technology in making pupil up to date and more productive member of society. Blended learning is one such initiative. The concept of the term blended learning differs in different context of time and place. This term has the traces of its growth during 2000. Gros, et al .(2016) gave evidence of its concept but the most celebrated ,well defined and concrete terminology had come with the publication of first handbook on blended learning authored by Bonk and Graham in the year 2006. Blended learning can be termed as the combination of face to face and computer mediated instructions. In the present context blended learning means integration of traditional classroom teaching with virtual online learning environment. The unprecedented outbreak of pandemic has resulted in the growth of research interest in this field for sustainability of education system. Many research are seen to be focused on virtual learning during pandemic, worldwide. Many studies are directed towards the use of blended learning and its effectiveness in domain of English as a second language. However, if teachers will adopt this method in an effective way than it can be a potent method to achieving holistic outcomes in the field of English as second language. Lu (2021) in his study adopted mixed method to show positive impact of blended learning environment in promoting critical thinking in different aspects.

Banditvilai (2016) in his study established that blended learning is positively influencing the student's language skills. His finding also shows that online platform increase student's motivation towards self-study and engagement. Subramanian (2015) survey of previous research work attempted to understand the characteristics and perspective of blended learning strategies in Indian context. It concluded that blended learning are very much useful and helpful in sustainable approach with the innovative process to meet the need of 21st century learners. Adas,et al.(2013) in their study work with University student by using MOODLE online platform. The study was conducted into experimental and control group. The findings of the study revealed improved academic score of student using blended mode. Improvement in spelling and grammar among student of experimental group was noted. Sejdiu (2014) in the study stated that the blended learning makes the student to adopt various learning styles

and skills. It has made the use of various interactive tools in offline mode of learning also. Every educational institutions follow certain curriculum. It plays a pivotal role in directing the activities in which pupils must be engaged to full fill the desired educational outcomes. Among all the integrated subjects involved in curriculum, language plays a significant role. Language is an effective medium to understand literature, science and philosophy. Learning of a language involves coding and decoding of signs and symbols in visible, audible or written forms to communicate. As far as learning of English as second language is concerned, it has the objective of developing life skills and literacy.

Importance of English as Second Language

Language is the most effective means of communication. In Indian context the study of English as second language is done in most of the states. Besides being the official language it is also the medium to connect with rest of the world. Even though there are languages like Mandarin, Spanish, and Arabic that are spoken by a lot of people, English is the most common second language, with 1.4 billion native and non-native speakers. That means that 20% of the world's population, or one in five people, can speak English. Not only is the fact that so many people speak English important, but so is the fact that English speakers can be found everywhere in the world, from the Americas to Asia, Africa, and Europe. People who don't speak English as their first language talk to each other a lot in English today. English is the language that connects people from all over the world. As a civilized world, many of us now travel around the world all the time. When people go on vacation to a foreign country, they often have to learn the local language or use English. For most people, English is the easiest and most useful choice. The study of English language will provide the students with opportunity to pursue higher education opportunities around the world. It is also helpful in seeking jobs worldwide. We all live in a global community that is bringing us much closer together, so we need to be able to talk to each other well. One of the essential aspect of English language is that it connects the whole world like a small global village through social media platform. The educational implication of English as a language make it an essential part of curriculum from grass root level. It opens up the window of information and knowledge resources to everyone.

Achieving Holistic outcomes through Blended Learning Strategies

Blended learning is a method that has become more popular in recent years as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic and the widespread use of digital technology in the learning process. Language studies have educational outcomes that nurture holistic development of pupils. The holistic outcome may be categorised into scholastic, personal and social domain of every learner. The scholastic or academic outcome aims at development of skills like listening, speaking, reading and writing. It comprises the understanding and application of the subject of study in different contexts. The academic outcome is measured in terms of achievement test scores on short and long term basis. Language studies also aims at development of personal traits. Knowledge of more than one language tends to boost self confidence among students. It helps in inculcating moral values by comprehending the world around us. The social aim comprises the study of language to promote social awareness among learners. This helps in development of effective communication skill which is very essential to pursue success in life. English language acquisition helps learner to gain cross cultural awareness as English is considered a global Language. Pupil can understand the similarities and differences in believe system of various cultures and can built up one's own concept and attitude towards them. The knowledge built the skill of adjustment among learners and the power of empathy in them. All the skill contributes towards the incubation of power of resilience. It improves the skill of cooperation. Language is medium of communication and study of English as second language connect the learner beyond the limitation of regional boundaries and become a global citizen. It has also been shown that blended learning can help students learn English better when they are learning English as a second language (ESL) (Damayanti & Sari, 2017; Ginaya, Rejeki, & Astuti, 2018).

Prerequisites of Blended Learning

Before commencing a new mode of teaching and learning in traditional environment it is very essential to acquaint teachers, parents and learners about its concept and function. There is a need of proper orientation to the stakeholders involved. To implement blended learning any how in any situation is not possible. It needs technical knowledge along with content knowledge. Expertise in the field of using Technology is the prerequisite of blended learning. Knowledge of various online tools and platform accounts for managing core study. Teacher's competency and learners digital literacy is needed. Selection of appropriate content to deliver lesson through hybrid mode needs proper planning beforehand by the teachers for an effective pedagogy.

The Use of Blended Learning in English language Learning Class

Use of blended learning in English language class can be done through various means but if the most available device to implement it is considered according to the economic status of Indian population, mobile phone is the most common option. Mobile apps, internet, web based learning, YouTube videos, recorded lectures, cloud classes platforms etc. are the medium for combining traditional face to face learning with the online platform. For example, to develop listening skills audio clips can be used in a class. Students can be asked to explain what they have listened in their own words which will develop their listening as well as speaking skill. YouTube videos related to study material may provide them with first-hand knowledge of the subject which can promote discussion among learners in real classroom situation. It will stimulate their critical thinking. Students should be provided with provision of collaborative work in the form of project. Here they can use the internet or web based learning to get information collected related to their subjects. They can work in group to accomplish task entirely according to their own thinking and ability. It gives boost to their creativity.

Benefits of Blended Learning in English as Second Language

Implementation of blended learning will bring more exposure to study material. If learners will have study material on their own device they can easily go through it number of times at their own pace. This definitely improves comprehensive skill. Students are able to look into a subject matter from different perspective. They do not rely on teachers and textbooks as the only source of knowledge. Blended learning in educational endeavour breaks the monotony of traditional education system and adds variety, to bag the interest of learners. It motivates the learners to be more focused towards study. It is very helpful in inculcating self-study habits among them. In real classroom situation there exists some students in class who sometimes lag behind due to less pace of learning ability. It represents the individual differences within a class, here use of recorded lectures can provide a solution to them.

Conclusion

Education aims at holistic development of a child considering every aspect of human existence in society. Learning language other than mother tongue itself delimits the learners from the constraints of regional boundaries and connect them to the whole world. If blended learning is incorporated and implemented in teaching and learning process of language studies, it will make learning more interesting and effective which will contribute to the fulfilment of desirable holistic outcome of education. Effective communication skill and social cultural awareness through language studies make them a productive member of the entire world. The combination of traditional and online mode through Blended learning improves digital literacy and competence to handle Technology in education for both teachers and learners. Language gives expression to human thought and ideas. It is very essential for development of not only listening, speaking, reading and writing skill but also life skills on the wider spectrum. With the fast growth of information technology, communication technology, and educational technology, the traditional way of teaching English in school is facing problems that have never been seen before. As blended learning has a lot of advantages over traditional education, which is why many people choose it. We can get the best results when teaching English as a second language when we use a blended approach.

References

- [1] Aborisade, P. A. (2013). Blended learning in English for academic purposes courses: A Nigerian
- [2] case study. In B. Tomlinson & C. Whittaker (Eds.), *Blended Learning in English Language Teaching: Course Design and Implementation*. London British Council, UK
- [3] Adas, D., & Bakir, A. (2013). Writing difficulties and new solutions: Blended Learning as an
- [4] approach to improve writing abilities. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(9), 254-266
- [5] Albiladi, W. S., & Alshareef, K. K. (2019). Blended learning in English teaching and
- [6] learning: A review of the current literature. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(2), 232. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1002.03>

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON BODY MASS INDEX AND SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE AMONG ADULT WOMEN SUFFERING WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARIAN SYNDROME

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Abstract

The goal of the random group experimental study was to determine the effect of yogic practices on BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure in Adult women with polycystic ovarian syndrome. It was hypothesized that yogic practices would result in significant differences in selected physiological variables such as BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure between Adult polycystic ovarian syndrome women and the control group. For the purpose of the study, 30 Adult polycystic ovarian syndrome women from Chennai were chosen at random using a random group sampling design, and they were divided into two groups A and B, each with 15 subjects. Before the start of the training program, the two groups (A and B) were given a pretest on the selected dependent variables. Group A received yogic practices, while Group B (Control Group) did not receive any treatment and was placed in active rest. After an eight-week experiment, the two groups (A and B) were retested on the same dependent variables as the posttest. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) method was used to determine the significant differences between the experimental and control groups. demonstrated that the experimental group differed significantly from the control group The study's findings demonstrated that yogic practices reduced both selected physiological variables such as BMI and systolic blood pressure in Adult women with polycystic ovarian syndrome. At 0.05 level of confidence, the hypothesis was accepted. As a result, it was concluded that yogic practices can help Adult with polycystic ovarian syndrome maintain a healthy BMI and Systolic Blood Pressure.

Keywords: *Yogic Practices, Blood Pressure, Systolic Blood Pressure, Body Mass Index*

Introduction

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a problem with hormones that happens during the reproductive years. If you have PCOS, you may not have periods very often. Or you may have periods that last many days. You may also have too much of a hormone called androgen in your body. With PCOS, many small sacs of fluid develop along the outer edge of the ovary. These are called cysts. The small fluid-filled cysts contain immature eggs. These are called follicles. The follicles fail to regularly release eggs. The exact cause of PCOS is unknown. Early diagnosis and treatment along with weight loss may lower the risk of long-term complications such as type 2 diabetes and heart disease. PCOS is a problem with hormones that affects women during their childbearing years (ages 15 to 44). Between 2.2 and 26.7 percent of women in this age group have PCOS (1, 2Trusted Source). Many women have PCOS but don't know it. In one study, up to 70 percent of women with PCOS hadn't been diagnosed (2Trusted Source). PCOS affects a woman's ovaries, the reproductive organs that produce estrogen and progesterone — hormones that regulate the menstrual cycle. The ovaries also produce a small amount of male hormones called androgens. The ovaries release eggs to be fertilized by a man's sperm. The release of an egg each month is called ovulation. Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH), which are produced in the pituitary gland, control ovulation. FSH stimulates the ovary to produce a follicle — a sac that contains an egg — and then LH triggers the ovary to release a mature egg. PCOS is a “syndrome,” or group of symptoms that affects the ovaries and ovulation. Its three main features are:

- 1) *Cysts in the ovaries*
- 2) *High levels of male hormones*
- 3) *Irregular or skipped periods*

In PCOS, many small, fluid-filled sacs grow inside the ovaries. The word “polycystic” means “many cysts.” These sacs are actually follicles, each one containing an immature egg. The eggs never mature enough to trigger ovulation. The lack of ovulation alters levels of estrogen, progesterone, FSH, and LH. Progesterone levels are lower than usual, while androgen levels are higher than usual. Extra male hormones disrupt the menstrual cycle, so women with PCOS get fewer periods than usual.

Objectives of the Study

The study's goal was to determine whether yoga practices on Adult polycystic ovarian syndrome would have any discernible effects on certain physiological indicators.

Purpose of the Study

The goal of the study was to determine how yoga practices affected Adult polycystic ovarian syndrome women's body mass index (BMI) and systolic blood pressure.

Hypothesis

It was predicted that adult women with polycystic ovarian syndrome would have significant BMI and systolic blood pressure differences from the control group as a result of yoga practices.

Delimitations

- 1) The subjects were middle aged polycystic ovarian syndrome women only.
- 2) The study was delimited to Adult women from Chennai city only
- 3) Age of subjects was ranged from 18 to 25 years only.
- 4) Independent variable was yogic practices only.
- 5) The dependent variables were restricted to Body Mass Index (BMI) and blood pressure (Systolic) only.

Review of Related Literature

Kumari, N Suchetha et. al., (2011) investigated a study on "Effect of yoga therapy on body mass index and oxidative status." Forty obese male and female were selected as subjects. The changes in body weight, body mass index, blood sugar, MDA level and total antioxidant status was estimated before and after one month of yoga therapy. The data was analyzed using paired't' test at 0.05 level of significance. Latha and KV Kalliappan (1991) conducted a study on Yoga, Pranayama, Thermal Biofeedback Techniques in the Management of Stress and High Blood Pressure. The sample of the study consisted of 14 essential hypertensive patients. Seven of these patients underwent training in yoga and thermal biofeedback technique for a period of six months. Other seven patients served as a comparison group. Results showed a significant reduction in the systolic blood pressure during treatment phases. Moderate reduction in the diastolic pressure was noticed, only when the thermal feedback was introduced. This also corresponded to significant reduction in the intake of anti-hypertensive drugs. Training in yoga and thermal biofeedback procedures were not effective in altering the perceptions associated with stressful experiences.

Methodology

For the purpose of the study, 30 *polycystic ovarian syndrome adult* women between the ages of 18 and 25 from Chennai were randomly chosen for the study. They were evenly divided into two groups, I and II, with 15 individuals in each group. Before the training programme began, the two groups (I and II) each took a preliminary test on the chosen dependent variable. For a total of eight weeks, Group I had daily 60-minute yoga sessions. During the experiment, Group II (the control group) was allowed to carry on with their regular activities and way of life without receiving any special instruction. The same selected dependent variable, the chosen physiological measures like Body Mass Index (BMI) and blood pressure, were once more rested on after eight weeks for the two groups (Systolic). To determine the significant differences between the experimental groups and the control group, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized. The level of confidence for the significance test was set at 0.05.

Results and Discussions

The data pertaining to the variable collected from the groups before and after the training period were statistically analyzed by using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant difference and the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value for the BMI (Body Mass Index) and Systolic blood pressure were greater than the table value, indicating that there was a significant difference among the post test and adjusted posttest means of the yogic practice group than the control group on physiological variables.

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Table I Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the Pre, Post and Adjusted Post Test Mean Values for Yoga Group and Control Group on BMI (Kg/M²)

Test	Experimental Group – I (yogic practices)	Control group	Source of variance	df	Sum of square	Mean square	F
Pre-test mean	24.63	25.54	Between	1	0.69	0.344	0.11
			Within	28	262.47	3.02	
Post-test mean	22.49	24.96	Between	1	362.40	181.20	53.69*
			Within	28	293.60	3.37	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. (Table F-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 1 & 28 (df) =4.21, 1 & 27 (df) =4.22)

Table I shows that the pre test mean scores of BMI of Experimental group I (yogic practices) was 24.63 and control group was 25.54. The post test means showed differences due to Six weeks of Yogic practices and mean values recorded were 22.49 and 24.96 respectively. The obtained F value on pre test scores 0.11 was lesser than the required F value of 3.1 to be significant at 0.05 level. This proved that there was no significant difference between the groups at initial stage and the randomization at the initial stage was equal. The post test scores analysis proved that there was significant difference between the groups as the obtained F value at 53.69 was greater than the required F value at 3.1. This proved that the differences between the post test mean at the subjects were significant. Taking into consideration the pre and post test scores among the groups, adjusted mean scores were calculated and subjected to statistical treatment. The obtained F value at 53.22 was greater than the required F value at 3.1. This proved that there was Significant differences among the means due to Six weeks of yogic practices and BMI on the physiological variable BMI

Figure 1 Bar Diagram Showing the Pre, Post Mean Values of Yoga Group and Control Group on BMI (Kg/m²)

The results of the study on the selected physiological variables showed that group I has significant differences on BMI (Body mass index) and Systolic blood pressure, due to yogic practices. Hence, the hypothesis was accepted at 0.05 level of confidence. The above findings were substantiated by the observations made by experts such as **Kumari, N Suchetha et. al., (2011)**

Computation Of Mean And Analysis Of Variance Of Systolic Blood Pressure Of Experimental And Control Group (mm/hg)

Test	Experimental Group (Yogic Practices)	Control group	Source of variance	Df	Sum of square	Mean square	F
Pre-test mean	141.1667	141.87	Between	1	24.16	12.078	0.88
			Within	28	1193.00	13.71	
Post-test	126.5	140.63	Between	1	3275.02	1637.51	125.12*

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mean			Within	28	1138.63	13.09	
			Within	27	1120.223	13.03	

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence. (The table value required for significance at 0.05 with df 1 and 38 and 1 and 37 are 4.10 and 4.11 respectively)

The obtained F value on pre test scores 0.88 was lesser than the required F value of 4.10 to be significant at 0.05 level. This proved that there was no significant difference between the groups a pre test and post test and the randomization at the pre test was equal. The post test scores analysis proved that there was significant difference between the groups, as obtained F value 125.12 was greater than the required F value of 4.11. This proved that the differences between the post test means of the subjects were significant. Taking into consideration the pre and post test scores among the groups, adjusted mean scores were calculated and subjected to statistical treatment.

Bar Diagram Showing Pre and Post-Test Mean Values of Control Group and Experimental Group on Systolic Blood Pressure

The results of the study on the selected physiological variable showed that group 1 has significant differences on blood pressure (systolic), due to yogic practices. Hence, the hypothesis was accepted at 0.05 level of confidence. The above finding can also be substantiated by the observations made by experts such as Nejati S. et.al, (2015)

Discussion on Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that there would be significant differences on selected Physiological variables such as BMI (Body mass index) and Systolic blood pressure due to yogic practices among adult women suffering with polycystic ovarian syndrome than the control group. The results proved that there were significant differences on Body mass index (BMI) and blood pressure (Systolic) (both decreased) due to yogic practices than the control group among adult women suffering with polycystic ovarian syndrome.

Conclusion

It is concluded that yogic practices decreased Body mass index (BMI) and blood pressure(systolic) significantly among adult women suffering with polycystic ovarian syndrome.

References

- [1] Shantakumari, Nisha, Sheifa Sequeira, and Rasha Eldeeb. c." Effect of yoga besed on polycystic ovarian syndrome 1.2 (2012): 60-63.
- [2] Latha and KV Kalliappan " Thermal Biofeedback Techniques in the Management of Stress and High Blood Pressure on Polycystic ovarian syndrome: a systematic review." Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine 4.4 (1991): 469-486.

TECHNOLOGY IN HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

Human learning process do not take place on nothing, but are based on idea, beliefs and views of the world that humans have of all things which is called a paradigm. The paradigm affects both the perception and the way humans act on things. Knowledge, therefore, has a variety of characteristics that require different learning processes, both in transferring knowledge and creating new knowledge. Education is an important process in the creation of knowledge so that human beings can develop themselves holistically. In addition, problems are found in teaching and learning of higher education institutions in important aspects: for example, teachers often teach in a lecture style, transfer knowledge in a way for learners to imitate. Moreover, in teaching and learning process, the focus is on memorization for exams rather than on students' thinking, analyzing and seeking knowledge. As a result, the learners are found lack of the inquisitive mind, and the learning is focused on theoretical subjects rather than practice, and lack of teaching and learning that are consistent with reality. Innovation in teaching media resulting from the advancement of computer technology makes educators try to use the potential of these technologies to produce several new teaching materials. Examples of teaching media innovations are CAI, multimedia, teleconference, instructional module and interactive video, etc.

Keywords: *Technology, Holistic Education, Etc.*

Introduction

“Enlightening minds, Encouraging creativity, Fostering responsibility.”

Every parent wants their child to excel not only in studies but also in life. And they need to know that this could only be achievable through some good experiences and learning. Hence, schools play a vital role in building a good base for the child. So, it is necessary to know how a different education system can help their child nurture. And that's why a new education approach of teaching is introducing nowadays which is Holistic Education. Holistic Education is an approach to teaching that focuses on the academics and social needs of students. The educators seek to fulfil the academics requirements of the students. And teach them the right methods by which they can face the challenges of life. They try to engage all aspects of the learner that includes the mind, spirit, and body. In this educational approach, the emphasis is on the positive environment of the schools. And also, on the thinking abilities of the students with their positive social behaviours.

Importance of Holistic Education

Holistic Education promotes social-awareness and a sense of responsibility with self-confidence among the students. It helps the students to develop strong critical thinking abilities and makes them exceptional at problem-solving.

Adopting a Holistic Approach to Technology in Education

Technology plays a very important role in helping everyone survive in this 21st century. Without it, one cannot imagine this world. Ever since Covid-19 happened, technology has proved to be a boon for the educational

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sector. Educators realised the role of digitisation a while ago but this pandemic gave it a sudden thrust and boost. Educators are striving to prepare their students for the 21st century workplace, most-often in the context of strained budgets, a lack of available IT resources and the demand for energy efficiency. Cloud services – often available at low to no cost – and shared-resource computing offer a way to address these challenges.

Innovative Holistic Educational Technology

1. Digital readers and tablets

Increasingly, schools are looking to replace the bulkier hard-copy textbooks with digital ones that are accessible via a tablet.

Pros

They eliminate the need for students to carry around a heavy backpack full of books.

They provide a centralized, accessible place for all reading materials.

The regular update of digital content eliminates the cost of purchasing new textbook editions every few years.

Apps added to tablets can meet the educational needs of the students and provide for more personalized learning opportunities.

Cons

To fully implement, schools would need to provide a tablet to every student and have a system in place for dealing with lost, damaged, or stolen assets. (However, a BYOD policy may be a feasible and more cost effective alternative.)

It eliminates the option for students to dramatically chuck their math book across the room when they get frustrated with it. (I feel that loss on a personal level.)

2. 3D printing

3D printing has already seen an impressive application in the world at large. According to Forbes, 3D printers have been able to create anything from car parts to artificial organs. In the classroom setting, 3D printing can create hands-on models that students can investigate and interact with. For example, students could learn about the geography of an area by observing a 3D map of it.

Pros

3D printing reaches both visual and kinesthetic learners.

It engages the students and gets them curious.

It reduces the time teachers need to spend on creating their own models (e.g., for a science class).

Cons

Barely any. One might argue that 3D printing technology means students won't get to create their own physical models, but there's nothing suggesting that the two can't coexist.

3. Virtual reality

Technology for virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality is rapidly developing. One of the primary uses for this technology in the classroom is to take students on virtual field trips to places otherwise inaccessible. For example, a student could take a virtual field trip to ancient Egypt or to the bottom of the ocean. One provider of this technology is Nearpod VR.

Pros

It provides engaging, real-life experiences that would otherwise be harmful or inaccessible.

Appeals to visual learners who like to see and experience things instead of merely reading about them.

Cons

Students using virtual reality may develop a lack of spatial awareness in the real world. In other words, they could hit or run into something in the real world while immersed in the virtual one.

Motion sickness can develop in some students due to their eyes sensing movement while their body does not.

4. Gamification

Students learn better when they're having fun. The use of gaming in the classroom applies this concept by tying together the fun part of play with the content and concepts that students must learn.

Pros

It increases student engagement.
It creates enthusiasm for the lesson.
It provides immediate feedback.

Cons

Not every fun game is effective at teaching a given concept. Not every game that is effective at teaching the concept is fun, either.

It takes time and training to learn how to effectively use games for learning. However, platforms like Classcraft use gaming technology and offer training for those who want to learn how to better implement it in their classrooms.

5. Cloud technology

The cloud hosts apps and services on the internet instead of being on a user's computer. It enables information to be stored, shared, and accessed on any device that's connected to the internet. In education, the cloud is used to store and share digital textbooks, lesson plans, videos, and assignments. It's also used to give students the opportunity to chat live with their instructors and other classmates. In a related vein, cloud technology is enabling a new educational model known as 'flipped classrooms' in which students can watch a lecture before class and spend the class time engaged in discussion, group work, and analytical activities.

Pros

It reduces the chances of homework getting lost between school and home.
It reduces the need for students to carry heavy textbooks.
It enables students to easily access information from any device connected to the internet.
It enables quick and easy access to the teacher through live chat options.

Cons

To fully adopt the cloud, schools would need to somehow ensure that every student has adequate access to the internet.

Security. Although pretty much every network on the cloud has a security system in place to protect its information, hacking can be a concern.

6. Artificial Intelligence

AI is making its way into the educational sphere by means of automating grading and feedback and providing personalized learning opportunities.

Pros

It can save the teacher time by doing the grading and giving feedback on their behalf.
It provides greater insights into a student's learning patterns.

Cons

Teachers can learn a lot about a student's learning patterns by doing the grading themselves.
There's a personal element of care when a teacher gives personalized feedback (rather than letting a machine generate one).

7. Mobile technology

Rather than banning cell phones and other mobile devices from use during class, some schools are incorporating this technology into the learning process through educational apps.

Pros

The wide variety of available apps offers the opportunity for students to engage in their own learning process.

Educational apps provide the opportunity to personalize learning to each student.

Cons

Not every student possesses a mobile device, and not every parent is comfortable with their child having one.

To really utilize this technology, schools would need to make sure that every parent is onboard and that every student has access to some sort of mobile device.

How has Technology improved Education?

1. Digital Simulations and Models

Digital simulations and models can help teachers more tangibly and clearly explain difficult concepts and

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can help students who are visual or tactile learners better understand the concepts. Digital simulations shine when they're directly applicable to their real-world counterparts.

2. You can Now Finish a Degree Online

For those that work all day and can't go to class in person, online education has been a stunning arrangement. From the ivy leagues to junior college, many different types of institutions offer online courses, certifications, and degrees.

3. Improved Communication

Ineffective correspondence among teachers and students can be a hindrance to learning and education. Technology can change the classroom into a network where teachers post assignments progressively, and students can ask questions more easily—of teachers and of their peers—and reference a structured record of past discussions.

4. Advanced Research, Quick Information, and eBooks

Cloud storage and smart search engines have made research a great deal less demanding for students nowadays. Gone are the days when they needed to flip through heaps of books to locate a specific reference. Since a considerable measure of time is spared amid research, and since it is easier to access a wider array of sources, students can consolidate a ton of information and knowledge in their projects. Results can be compared worldwide more efficiently, allowing for faster progress in advanced research. eBooks and learning apps are incredible resources, but near useless to students without the hardware to use them.

5. Effective Assessments

There is programming accessible with which teachers can give or get assessments of their students continuously. Digital assessments allow teachers to check in on progress regularly. They then have the ability to keep records up to date more easily and accurately. They can tell teachers not only whether the student got a question right, but also how much time was spent on the question. These assessments give teachers a much clearer picture as to their students' advancement. From there, they can intervene in a timelier, effective manner. They may also be able to analyze trends across the class, and more easily compare test results with other classrooms and schools.

6. Learning at One's Own Pace

Obviously, self-guided learning is another enormous advantage that students appreciate with the rise of technology in the education industry. Despite the fact that there are some quick students who are fit for adjusting to new concepts quickly, there are others who must set aside considerable time to assimilate a thought.

7. Fun Learning

Any good teacher will tell you student engagement is key in a meaningful learning experience. Active participation and attention can turn a lesson into something truly memorable. Game-based learning is a field that is becoming far more widespread and is studied extensively.

8. Online Group Collaboration

The idea of group study has been improved in the digital world. Presently, students don't have to get together physically; there are many ways to collaborate online. They can share files and notes, work together on documents, instant message or email. They can even use video conferencing to discuss projects face to face.

9. Open Education

We have access to information like never before. In this innovative and revolutionized world, there are various free resources available to learners—whether they are articles written by individuals, micro-learning courses from experts, or archives made available by prestigious colleges. Regardless of your location or budget, if you have internet access, the universe of the web will undoubtedly have the means to answer your question.

Conclusion

Technological advancements are truly impressive. We should accept that this is the world our students are growing up in and provide opportunities to expose them to these wonderful developments. However, each new technology should be carefully evaluated and used as a tool to enhance the personal element in the teaching process, not to completely replace traditional learning methods. According to a poll conducted by the School of Education, 75% of educators believed that textbook learning will be superseded by digital content learning. To assuage the learners towards technology-driven methods, certain technology marvels are on-trend nowadays. Many organizations are realizing that students need more than just a strong foundation in a core curriculum, they also need to be supported by a community and to develop a compassionate understanding of the world around them. As technology has rooted its way into our day-to-day existence, education has been changed. With information at the tips of our fingers, learning is now boundless. Technology can be utilized to improve teaching and learning and help our students be successful.

Reference

- [1] Ron Miller, 1999, A Brief Introduction to Holistic Education.
- [2] "What is Holistic Education? A Deep Insight - Holistic Canvas". 2023-01-12. Retrieved 2023-01-14.
- [3] Fowlers, J 1998, 'Problem solving in technology education: A Taoist perspective', *Journal of Technology Education*, vol.10, no.1.
- [4] Hegel, G W F & Miller, A V 1989, *Hegel's science of logic*, Humanities Press International, Atlantic Highlands, NJ.
- [5] Ihde, D 1979, *Technics and praxis*, Dordrecht, Holland; D. Reidel Pub. Co., Boston.
- [6] Matthews, M R. n.d., 'The epistemology of early Marx', Lecture 18, Sydney: UNSW, School of Education, lecture notes distributed in 1985.
- [7] Peters, R S 1971, *Ethics and education*, Scott, Foresman and Co., USA.
- [8] Seemann, K W & Talbot, R 1995, 'Technacy: Towards a holistic understanding of technology teaching and learning among aboriginal Australians', *Prospects*, vol.XXV, no.4.
- [9] Speake, J 1979, *A dictionary of philosophy*, The MacMillan Press, London.

THE ART OF REWIRING THE BRAIN WITH PRACTICE AND POSITIVE EMOTIONS FOR MENTAL HEALTH : A HOLISTIC APPROACH

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Abstract

Traditionally the focus of mental health work with children and young people, including those seen as having behaviour problems and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), has been on the individual child or young person, and specifically on the identification, referral and treatment of their problem. This is now changing, and child mental health work is starting to take a more holistic and preventive approach. Nowadays there is an argument for a more holistic approach to promote mental health with learning and practice of positive emotions. The main aim is to encourage more research on positive aspects of mental health by a closer study on the negativity bias brain. To this end, the paper provides a holistic approach of developing an individual's mental health with the art of rewiring the brain. Generally, someone's brain is being hard-wired to focus on negative things and this may be probably because of the diverse response systems of the brain counting those identified with emotional, cognitive and social behavior. If there is a question of whether someone can reprogram and rewire the brain, then the answer would be that someone's brains can change physically, as a result of learning and practice of positive emotions. As such, practicing a positive habit can incline someone's thoughts to be increasingly affirmative. This paper is an attempt to conceptually relate the positive thinking and the neuroplasticity of brain with a holistic approach.

Keywords: *Holistic Approach, Mental Health, Negativity Bias, Brain, Neuroplasticity*

Introduction

There exists a propensity for people to give more consideration to negative information than to positive information and it can be called as the negativity bias. It has been identified that negative occasions inspire more rapid and more prominent reactions than non-negative occasions. Generally, someone's brain is being hard-wired to focus on negative things and this may be probably because of the diverse response systems of the brain counting those identified with cognitive, emotional, and social behavior. When this being the undesirable state, is it possible to change someone's negativity bias into optimistic or positive thinking so as to design a constructive life. Certainly, with the capacity of the brain to design itself as desired through continuous learning and practice. The human brain has a stunning capacity to rearrange itself by shaping new associations between brain cells or neurons and is called as neuroplasticity of brain. Particularly, someone's thought process affects the neural network of the brain involving chemical transmissions between neurons of the brain. Neuroscientific research emphasize on how positive and negative thoughts influence the development and advancement of these supernatural neurons and their synaptic intersections. Also the human brain can be rewired or reprogrammed as desired with the practice and emotions of positive thinking.

The Negativity Bias Brain

The human brain has undergone an evolution resulting with a "negativity bias," says mindfulness master Mc Garvey, an instructor at the Harvard Graduate School of Education. A large portion of the literature underpins the presence of a Negativity bias. To understand simply, the negativity bias can be stated as the tendency for people to give more consideration to negative information than to positive information. Rozin & Royzman (2001) checked on proof that negative information is more notable than positive information that risen up out of a range of mental, literary, religious and cultural sources. The authors depicted four mechanisms that support their theory that negative information is handled uniquely in contrast to positive information, including its potency, steeper gradients wherein the reactions being swifter, negative strength when weighing both the negative and positive information and negative differentiations wherein negative elements appears more conceptually complex. Behavioral studies emphasize that there exists a 'negativity bias' in the method for any of the occasions encompassing is being handled. Especially, it has been demonstrated that negative occasions inspire more rapid and furthermore more prominent reactions than non-negative occasions. This 'negativity bias' is showed through

assorted reaction frameworks, including those identified with cognitive, emotional and social conduct (Peeters and Czapinsky, 1990; Taylor, 1991; Mogg and Bradley, 1998;Cacioppo and Gardner,1999; Mogg et al., 2000)

Positive Thinking Rewiring The Brain: A Cyclic Process

Daniel Goleman creator of “Focus: The Hidden Driver of Excellence” says that the human brain has increased prefrontal action and energy bringing about improved mental capacities, for example, imaginative reasoning, intellectual adaptability, and significantly quicker preparing. Moreover Goleman states that positive feelings really extend our range of consideration and it additionally changes our recognition and spotlight on a greater amount of the "we" rather than the "me". Investigating the prefrontal cortex, when happy thoughts do occurs, there is brain development through the support and generation of new neural connections. The prefrontal cortex is where; all brain capacities conjugate and after that are dispensed to different parts of the mind or transmitted to different parts of the body. The prefrontal cortex is the exchanging station that controls the signs from the neurons as well as enables somebody to reflect and consider what the person in question is doing at the time. It enables an individual to control feelings through the profound limbic brain. Since it enables the individual to focus, it additionally gives time for meta-cognition which is nothing but being aware of one's very own manners of thinking. There exists two major key points, both of which are essential for understanding the art of rewiring brain. One is Practice and the other being emotions.

Figure 3: A Holistic & Cyclic Approach for Mental Health with practice and emotions.

Conclusion

Thus a holistic approach encompassing different areas like negativity bias brain, the neuroplasticity nature of brain, thinking that affect the neural network, positive thinking and repetition packed with feelings results in desired behaviors or habits and positive habits are helpful in reprogramming and rewiring the brain as desired for a constructive design of life. Recently, as most of the neuroscientific research has a greater emphasis on meta-cognition, this review can also be projected to a quantitative research involving experimental study so as to enhance the modeling in artificial neural network.

References

- [1] Weare, K. (2006). Taking a positive, holistic approach to the mental and emotional health and well-being of children and young people.
- [2] Koslander, T., da Silva, A. B., & Roxberg, Å. (2009). Existential and spiritual needs in mental health care: An ethical and holistic perspective. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 27(1), 34-42.
- [3] Iman, R., Leah, S. (2016). The Biology of positive habits. Harvard Graduate School of Education.

CHALLENGES OF TRIBAL EDUCATION IN NORTH-EAST INDIA

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Abstract

Education is the most essential element for the enhancement of any country. For this, education structure needs to ensure the advantage of education to all people of the nation, removing the disparities irrespective of category, religion, caste, sex and geographical location. If we overlook all over the world, the status of schedule Caste and schedule tribes are backward in compared with the other people. The term tribal came from 'tribe' which refers to a class of human social group. According to some studies on tribal education the tribal community especially who live in North Eastern region of India are neglected by others. In every aspect of development, the government policy maker of our country make plan for them, but sorrowfully these communities are unable to make them in the same level with the mainstream of the society. This study tried to find out the drawbacks of this tribe particularly in the aspect of education. The study also clarify the cause behind the backwardness of educational status related to socio-economic condition, academic cause and personal cause of students from primary to higher education stage. From time to time government implemented various plans and schemes for tribal education. This study also tries to give some suggestion for development of tribal education. And finally the findings of the present study would be helpful to tribal education for giving suitable guideline about all-purposes of education. The study deals particularly with the tribes of North East India in regard to education of all three stages and carries out the present status of it.

Keywords: *Issues and Challenges, Education, North-East India, Schedule Tribe*

Introduction

Education is the most essential element for the improvement of any country. It makes an individual able to manage the problems of the nation and the society. Education is renowned as a tool for designing changes in a systematic manner and it is fundamentally concerned with every person as well as community development. It inculcates skills and competencies financially. The Indian constitution preserves justice, socio-economic and political equality of position and prospect to all citizens. For this, education structure needs to ensure the advantage of education to all people of the nation, removing the entire disparities irrespective of category, religion, caste, sex and geographical location. The right to education of every individual is one of the primary requirements of the 'Universal Declaration of Human Rights -1948' and 'International Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights -1966', Article 13 and 14. However, education is mostly neglected in the societies to meet the needs and demands of their members. Now a day, education is making more significant as planners and policy makers recognized it as input in shaping the rate of development. If we overlook all over the world the status of schedule caste and schedule tribes are backward compared with the other people. In every aspect of development the policy maker of every country make plan for them from time to time, but they are unable in making them equal with the mainstream of the society.

Tribal People and Tribal of North-Eastern Region of India

The term tribal came from 'tribe' which refers to a class of human social group. They are also known as indigenous people since they have a self identification with common and unique characteristics and social norms which distinguish them from other people of the society. The lifestyle of these ethnic groups may vary on the basis of their geographical location. They share characteristics of unity with each other, their earlier period and the territory they exist on. In our nation Tribal people are often denoted as native people, ethnic group, first nations, aboriginal people, adivasi, janajati, hill tribes, or hunter-gatherers etc. All over the world there are more than 476 million aboriginal people existing in 90 countries crosswise the world, accounting for 6.2 % of the universal population. An estimate of approximately 5000 indigenous ethnic group found throughout the world. Our nation comprises the second largest tribal inhabitants in the world. As per the census 2011 data, the tribal demography constitutes about 8.9 percent of the total population of the country. There are 705 indigenous group found in India with an estimated demography of 104 million. NE India includes 8 states which are Manipur, Meghalaya, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Mizoram, Tripura, Nagaland and Sikkim. In accordance to census 2011, out of 457.74

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lakh total inhabitants 126.79 lakh (27.7%) were tribal of NE India. There are 145 various ethnic groups with assorted social and cultural lives in N E India, where 78 groups are found in very large amount from survey data. One of the typical features of schedule tribes is that the conventional of them live in extend habitations located in remote, interior, and distant hilly and forest areas of North East India. The culture, nature, traditions, language, norms, believes and values are different in every ethnic group. Majority of the indigenous groups express themselves by variety of languages (Verbal Communication) which are different from the language spoken in the area of the state where they are to be found. There are more than 100 such languages and dialects found in North East region of India. As per geographical location, the tribes of N E region of India divided in two categories as hill tribes and plain tribes. The main tribal group of North East India which have more than 5000 population are-Bodo, Koch-Rajbanshi, Angami, Ao, Chakma, Dimasa, Reang, Konyak, Adi, Misimi, Aka, Garo, Mishing, Galong, Nishi, Wancho, Khasi, Tangkhul, Karbi, Tripuri, Lusai, Mizo, Kuki, Apatani, Jaintia, Singpho, Angami, Deori, Kachari, Bhutia, Barmans, Hmar, Rabha, Lepcha, Lakher, etc.

Educational Status among the Tribes of North-East India

In pre-independent period the Christian Missionary plays a vital role in spread and development of tribal people especially in the aspect of health and education all over the nation. But they were able to succeed mostly in Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and greater Assam, which is now divided into seven state of North East India. After that in various time the status of education among north eastern tribe go through up and down. Now-a-day the literacy rate of North East India shows slightly lower than the rest of country. Since North East India comprises mostly tribal inhabitant.

Table-01 Demographic data of North eastern state (Census data-2011)

States	Overall		Tribal	
	Population	Literacy Rate	Population	Literacy Rate
Arunachal Pradesh	13,82,611	65.38%	951,821	64.58%
Assam	3,11,69,272	72.19%	3,884,371	72.06%
Manipur	27,21,756	76.9%	1,167,422	72.58%
Meghalaya	29,64,007	74.43%	2,555,861	74.53%
Mizoram	10,91,014	91.58%	1,036,115	91.51%
Nagaland	19,80,602	79.55%	1,710,973	80.04%
Sikkim	610,577	82.20%	206,360	79.74%
Tripura	36,71,032	87.22%	1,166,813	79.05%

Historical Perspective and Government Schemes for Tribal Education

After independent our constitution and government come in force and give special attention to the education and development of every citizen. According to 86th amendment of constitution, Article 21(A) incorporates the right of children to free and compulsory education between the age group of 6-14 years. It is in accordance with the requirements of the RTE Act 17. Under Article 15(4) and 46, central as well as state government has established primary, middle and high school for tribal inhabitant. A large number of charitable organizations have come ahead in tribal areas for the function of educational development in those areas. In the first five year plan (1951-56) the government has taken much initiative for tribal development. Special Multipurpose Tribal Development Projects (MTDPs) were created at the end of plan (1954), Tribal Development Blocks (TBD) s was adopted in third five year plan period (1961-1966) and Tribal Sub-plan Strategy (TSP) in 1972 was enforced by the Ministry of Education and Social Welfare. Some of the important intervention taken by government for fulfillment of the need of tribal education such as- Pre and Post Metric Scholarship Scheme for STs, Pradhan Mantri Vanbandhu Vikas Yojana and Pradhan Mantri Janjatiya Vikas Mission for economic empowerment, Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship Scheme for ST students, Pradhan Mantri Adi Adarsh Gram Yojna (PNAAGY) for improvement of infrastructure, Mission Indradhanush and Nikshay Mitra Initiative (TB treatment) for better health, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana and Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana for holistic welfare of tribal communities, Vocational Training Centre etc. The National Policy of Education-1986 gives a board policy structure for eradication of illiteracy which was in very large number in between the tribal population at that time and sets a target of expenditure on education at 6% of the GDP. The 12th five year plan (2012-17) propose umbrella scheme for establishing 'Ashram School'. As a result there is 892 'Ashram Schools' established

which was purely residential across the country only for the development of schedule tribe students.

Challenges of Tribal Education in North East India

There are various problems and challenges face by the tribal population world wide as well as in North East India. In the education sector problems and challenges may be face by the people who are engage with the system, but the problems of tribal people are somewhat different from the rest of the general society. Some of these issues and challenges are as follows-

SOCIO-ECONOMIC: - In accordance to Economic Survey of India the Schedule tribe people have a poor socio-economic position. They are dependent on the nature and ecological conditions for their persistent existence. They suffer in low conditions and backwardness along with poverty. The society is also responsible for hindrance in education of tribal community students which known to be social cause like as- illiterate parents, lack of supervision and guidance at home, uncongenial home environment, marriage in the early age of life, bad company, juvenile delinquency, blind faith or believe in superstition, believe in dian or black soul, exploitation, mental pressure or distress, migration from one place to another, natural disaster, lack of communication and transportation, lack of awareness of their right, large family size or uncontrolled birth rate etc. Socio- economic condition of these tribal groups on a daily basis stands as partition for their development in every direction.

ACADEMIC: - New Education Policy 2020 provides more priority on tribal education but it is extreme away from proper accomplishment. Dropout, stagnation, distance of school from home, tough evaluation system, lack of co-ordination between teachers and parents, unattractive curriculum, syllabus not accordance to tribal area or environment, lack of tribal development and education policies, repeated failure of students, inflexible timetable of school hours, unattractive school environment and infrastructure, lack of teachers, problem for medium of instruction, untrained teachers, fear of teachers, unattractive instructional methods, inadequate teaching-learning strategies, lack of provision for co-curricular activities, lack of proper fund from government as well as from Tribal Affairs, shortage of learning materials, inadequate training facility for teachers, pitiable administrative functions, inadequate scholarship, holidays are not accordance to tribal economy etc. are some academic barrier identified as causes of education in primary, secondary and higher level. Indian education design of is always good quality for the average society of the country but for the weaker division its need some modifications.

PERSONAL: - Personal factors are beliefs or behavior specific to a student, like personality and interest. School comprises of different students with different personality and behavior. They can face a variety of problems for which they cannot adjust themselves with the school environment as well as the whole education system. The success and development of any work is depends upon the personal factor of an individual. In the education system also personal causes plays a vital role for succeeding it in the all stages.

Suggestions for Upgradation of Tribal Education

Tribal education system should have some changes and consideration to make them equal with the society. This changes in education policies can only make the tribal people interest in every stages of education. Some of these are as follows- literacy campaigns, attitude of the elderly individual, relevant study materials in local languages, appointment of local teachers and female teachers, stipends and various scholarships, residential schools and colleges, provide social security specially for the girls students, proper monitoring, equal opportunities, reduction in the household responsibilities, stop crime activities in schools, stop early marriages, create interest in study, provide free food opportunity, provide proper guidance and counseling etc.

Educational Implications of the Study

Education is the groundwork for the development of every people of the country. It is also essential for the overall development of human capital. Each research study procedure has some educational implications, in the same way the present study has been educative in nature in the areas of the tribal of North East India, quality of education in NE Region, improve in terms of tribal education, enrichment of information and ability to conduct action research. The study has its educative value in solving the problems face by the tribal people of NE region at the all stages of education. The work is an eye opener for the educational planners, educational administrators, policy maker and community members in improving the system for ensuring the quality of education for this section of the country. The findings of the present study would be helpful to tribal education for giving suitable guideline in all stages of education.

Conclusion

Education is the most important agent in the process of development and tribal education is utmost important not only for economic development but also for the inner strength of the community to meet new challenges in daily life. There is an imperative need for different government interventions, policy makers and planners to address this problem and assign more funds in the central and state educational budgets for expansion of tribal education. The tribal youths should be more engage in every activity of society and school, so that they can show their hidden talents and capabilities. There should be appropriate development of the curriculum, medium of instruction, instructional methods and teaching-learning methods, so that the tribal children feel motivated towards achievement of education.

References

- [1] Biswas, N.B. (2006) *Education in North East India, Delhi*- Shipra Publications.
- [2] Brahmanandam, T. & Babu, T.B. (2016). *Educational Status among the Scheduled Tribes*:
- [3] Kapur R (2019) *Challenges of Education amongst the Tribals in India*, Pdf download from www.researchdate.net

ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS' AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT TO THEIR PROFESSION

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Abstract

Physical Education teacher is to be responsible for planning, teaching and guiding children in a school setting. They teach a range of different sports, and provide young people with an opportunity to develop and improve their social and physical skills. The role of a Physical Education teacher is to facilitate this, helping children learn all about sport, increase their physical literacy, and develop important motor skills. For a lot of children, physical education can be one of their favourite lessons because they get to be active, sometimes outside, and competing in sporting activities with each other. The purpose of the study was to analyze the physical education Teachers, Affective commitment towards their profession. Totally three hundred and seventy-four (374) physical education teachers were subjects as selected randomly from South Districts of Tamilnadu, India, their age ranged from 23 – 55 years were selected in various schools like Government, Government Aided and Private sectors. The Tool of this Survey, Work Commitment towards their profession was developed by Allen & Meyer (1996) is a five-point Likert type scale were used. The collected data was analyzed by using the statistical technique of one-way ANOVA and where ever the F value found significant, Post hoc test was used with the help of statistical package for social science (SPSS). The mean values of Affective Commitment among Government School, Government Aided School and Private School are 22.25, 24.02 and 23.53 respectively. the obtained 'F' value was 6.180 which were greater than the required table value df 2 and 371 is 3.02, likewise the obtained significant level was ($p < 0.05$). it was showed that there was a significant difference exists in Affective Commitment among the Physical Education Teachers, therefore the scheffe's post hoc test was applied to find out the significant mean difference. The mean difference of Affective Commitment among the three different types of Schools were 1.769, 1.278 and 0.492 respectively. The mean difference value between Government and Government Aided are 1.769, which are higher than the confidence interval level 1.51 at 0.05 level of confidence. This result indicates a significant difference on Affective Commitment was found between the Physical Education Teachers who is working in government and government aided schools. However, the mean value of government aided school was found better than private Schools physical education teachers. and Private school was better than the government schools on Affective Commitment. It was concluded that the government aided school was better when compared to government aided and private schools in affective commitment.

Keywords: *Physical Education Teacher, Affective Commitment, Private School.*

Physical Education

Physical Education develops the skills, knowledge, values and attitudes needed for establishing and enjoying an active and healthy lifestyle, as well as building student confidence and competence in facing challenges as individuals and in groups or teams, through a wide range of learning activities. Physical Education is offered as an elective examination subject at senior secondary education level. Physical education teachers hold the main responsibility in conducting different educational activities. Therefore, they must obtain the need knowledge as well as skills which are the main requirements in teaching. Therefore, taking care of education is the first step in reforming education and providing teachers with needed competencies is the most efficient method in improving learning especially in physical education (Al-tamimi, 2009).

Commitment an Introduction

Commitment is important for teachers because it reflects a personal interpretation of work experience as absorbing and meaningful. It is a significant factor in efforts to improve school outcomes, especially student academic achievement (Kushman 1992). There are four "matters" commonly associated with teacher commitment: profession, student learning and the community.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is defined as a multidimensional concept that includes belief in and acceptance of the organization's goals and values; willingness to exert effort on the organization's behalf; and a desire to remain in the organization. Globally, governments, voluntary agencies, non-governmental organizations and individuals commit significant resources towards building and developing teacher professionalism. The need for improving teachers' job satisfaction and commitment has been considered paramount since almost half of the new teachers left the profession in the first five years. Indeed, teaching is classified as profession and a social service for national development, not simply an occupation aimed at making money for livelihood. A teacher should be permanently committed to his work. Therefore, checking the commitments of teacher is reasonable and timely to make education more desirable (Mowday et al 1982). Jeffrey, J. Bagrain (2003) maintains that "affective commitment develops if employees are able to meet their expectations and fulfil their needs within the organization." Affective commitment results in employees staying within an organization because they want to, and according to Romzek (1990), these employees will generally act in the organization's best interest and are less likely to leave the company.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to find out the Physical Education Teachers Affective Commitment towards their Profession.

Methodology

The purpose of the study was to analyze the physical education Teachers, Affective commitment towards their profession. To achieve the purpose of this study, totally three hundred and seventy-four (374) physical education teachers were subjects as selected randomly from South Districts of Tamilnadu, India, their age ranged from 23 – 55 years were selected in various schools like Government, Government Aided and Private sectors. The Tool of this Survey, Work Commitment towards their profession was developed by Allen & Meyer (1996) is a five-point Likert type scale were used. The information was gathered from the participants using a "Google form" that was delivered to them online. The collected data was analyzed by using the statistical technique of one-way ANOVA and where ever the F value found significant, Post hoc test was used with the help of statistical package for social science (SPSS). The data collected from the subjects were treated statistically.

Analysis and Discussions

Table – 1 Mean, standard deviation and ANOVA value of affective commitment in type of schools

Mean ± Standard Deviation			Affective Commitment	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Govt.	Govt. Aided	Private	Between Groups	200.106	2	100.053	6.180*
22.25 ± 4.036	24.02 ± 4.128	23.53 ± 3.922	Within Groups	6006.688	371	16.191	

(Note= * Significant at 0.05 level. P<0.05)

The above table shows the mean values of Affective Commitment among Government Schools, Government Aided Schools and Private Schools are 22.25, 24.02 and 23.53 respectively. An analysis of variance scores for Affective Commitment among the Physical Education Teachers were presented from the above table, the obtained 'F' value was 6.180 which were greater than the required table value df 2 and 371 is 3.02, likewise the obtained significant level was (p<0.05). The analysis of variance found to be significant, therefore the scheffe's post hoc test was applied to find out the significant mean difference among the teachers working in government, government aided and private schools. The scheffe's post hoc test of attitude on teachers working in government, government aided and private sector schools were presented in the table 2.

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Table – 2 Scheffe’s Post Hoc test for Analysis of Affective Commitment among Physical Education Teacher’s in different type of Schools

Mean Values			Mean Difference	Confidence Interval
Government Schools	Government Aided Schools	Private Schools		
22.25	24.02		1.769*	1.51
22.25		23.53	1.278	1.51
	24.02	23.53	0.492	1.53

(Note= *. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level)

The result of the above table shows that the mean difference of Affective Commitment among the three different types of School in Government-Government Aided, Government-Private and Government Aided-Private Schools were 1.769, 1.278 and 0.492 respectively. The mean difference value between Government and Government Aided are 1.769, which are higher than the confidence interval level 1.51 at 0.05 level of confidence. This result indicates a significant difference on Affective Commitment was found between the Physical Education Teachers who is working in government and government aided schools. However, the mean value of government aided school was found better than government Schools physical education teachers. But the mean value of affective commitment between Government-Private and Government Aided-Private Schools were 1.278 and 0.492 respectively which were lesser than the confidence interval level 1.51 and 1.53 at 0.05 level of confidence. This result indicates no significant difference on Affective Commitment was found between the government and private schools, government aided and private schools.

Discussion of Findings

Analyzed the Affective Commitment of government, government aided and private school physical education teachers, the significant difference was found among them. The mean difference value of government aided school PE teachers was better than government and private school PE teachers in Affective commitment. The result indicates no significant difference on Affective Commitment was found between the government and private schools, government aided and private schools.

References

- [1] Al-tamimi, Y. (2009). Physical education lesson and its effect on secondary school student’s trends in 1994-1995. *Sport Sciences Journal*, Vol (8), Issue (1).
- [2] Jeffrey, J. Bagraim. (2003). The dimensionality of professional commitment. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, Vol 29, No 2. P.no 6-9.
- [3] Kushman, J. W. (1992). The organizational dynamics of teacher workplace commitment: A study of urban elementary and middle schools. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, Vol. 28(1), pp. 5-42
- [4] Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89.
- [5] Mowday, R. T., Steers, R. M., & Porter, L. (1982). *Employee-Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism and Turnover*, San Diego, CA: Academy Press.
- [6] Romzek, B.S. (1990). Employee investment and commitment: The ties that bind. *Public Administration Review*, 50, 374-382.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

HOLISTIC EDUCATION THROUGH EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND COMPASSION AMONG B.ED TEACHER TRAINEES

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Abstract

Holistic education aims at all round development of body, mind and soul. It is the way imparting education to all the dimension of growth and development namely physical, social, emotional, moral and intelligence. All the dimensions of growth is essential in holistic education. This article focuses on the emotional and social aspect of the learners especially teacher trainees. Emotional development is discussed with the variable emotional intelligence and social development is discussed with compassion. Both emotional intelligence and compassion contributes towards holistic development of learner apart from academic achievement. Emotional intelligence is the ability to control one's emotions and understand to other's emotions. Emotional intelligence of the teacher trainees is indeed required to perform a task practically. Compassion is the ability to look into other's problems and understanding the feelings and sufferings of others and it is essentially a social skills.

Keywords: *Holistic Education, Emotional Intelligence, Compassion*

Introduction

Holistic education emerged in ancient Greek and indigenous cultures. Jan Christian smuts was the proponent of holistic education and emphasis on holism in United States on America. Holistic education is constructed on the Rs namely: Relationship, Responsibility and reverence to life. In holistic children or learner has to learn about themselves and it involves self-esteem, self-respect and it forms the first step. In the second step learners have to learn about the social literacy and emotional literacy, i.e. learning to form relationship with others and with having a balance of emotions. The third step is having ability to overcome difficulties and hardships in life. Final fourth step is about developing aesthetics which involves appreciation of beauty around them.

Important Variables for Holistic Education

In the holistic education, several variables are involved and out of which emotional and social growth and development are of much important as it involves in the second level of learning of the learners.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, assess, and control emotions. The term emotional intelligence has been routed from the social intelligence, which was first coined by E.L.Thonidike in 1920. Emotional quotient (EQ) is used interchangeably with "Emotional Intelligence". "Emotional Intelligence" involves the ability to access and or generate feelings. When they facilitates thoughts, the ability to regulate emotions to the mental ability of the organism. But this definition is hardly comprehensive for the present situation. A more formal academic definition refers to emotional awareness and reason so as to maximize long-term happiness. Mayer and Salovey (1997).

Meaning of Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence is the application of psychological resources in control of one's emotions. It is a form of intelligence relating to the emotional side of life, such as the ability to recognize and manage one's own and others' emotions, to motivate oneself and restrain impulses, and to handle interpersonal relationships effectively. This construct was originated by Daniel Goleman and latter several authors have explored in it. The main aim of Emotional Intelligence is the control over impulses that is prevalent in the environment and to deal effectively with emotions of one's life. The term Emotional Intelligence implies the intersection of emotion and cognition.

Compassion

Compassion is the ability to show empathy towards the problem or suffering of the individuals. It is the ability to alleviate the distress of others. Compassion is lined with empathy, sympathy, pity, concern, sensitivity, tenderness.

Elements of compassion

There are five elements of compassion namely

- 1) Recognizing Suffering: It is the ability to recognize that some one is suffering. It is the perceiving the suffering of one person.
- 2) Understanding the universality of human suffering: It the state of understanding that all human undergo different forms of suffering at different times of life.
- 3) Feeling for the person suffering : It is the emotional connection with the person who is suffering.
- 4) Tolerating uncomfortable feelings : It is the tolerance one posses when he or she faces uncomfortable and difficult feelings.
- 5) Motivation to alleviate suffering: It is the action taken to reduce the suffering.

Signs of compassion Some of the common signs of compassion are

- 1) Feeling of altruism
- 2) Understanding the feeling of what other people are undergoing through the pain of suffering
- 3) Understanding other people's emotions and pain
- 4) Taking action when someone's is suffering.
- 5) Having highly level of emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

Holistic education focuses on providing education covering all the dimension of growth and development. If the student teachers are provided with holistic education by providing emotional and social literacy, then could develop into holistic individuals with balanced personality.

References

- [1] lara Strauss, Billie Lever Taylor, Jenny Gu, Willem Kuyken, Ruth Baer, Fergal Jones, Kate Cavanagh. What is compassion and how can we measure it? A review of definitions and measures, Clinical Psychology Review, Volume 47, 2016, Pages 15-27

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

HOLISTIC HEALTH AND EDUCATION – A STEP FORWARD THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION FOR PRIMARY CHILDREN, TEACHER AND WOMEN

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Abstract

Through this study it is aimed to know the multiple criteria of primary children, teachers and women for holistic health and holistic education as a step forward through physical education. In our society teacher plays an important role. Teachers are the pillars to support the past, present, future generation of our society. So, being as a teacher they must be adaptive and updated in their knowledge towards the trend and modern world. Since being updated in a knowledge and knowing the importance of holistic health and education is must. Holistic education and health through physical education and physical activity can give a enormous reappearance in health maintenance and awareness of the healthy life style for primary children as they are the future builders of society and also for women as they are the care taker of their family likely children, parents, spouse as they are upcoming from there four wall life style and also as a each and every one. Its focuses on many dimension aspect of the Individual, Intellectual, Physical, Spiritual, Emotional Balance, Social Well Being, Cognitive Thinking, Cross Motor , Fine Motor ,Self Help, etc. So primary children, teachers, women have enormous benefit through holistic health and holistic education a step forward through physical education and physical activity.

Keywords: *Holistic Health, Holistic Education, Physical Education, Primary Children*

Introduction

In this modern daily lifestyle, we people are more connected to the electronic gadgets by known or unknowingly neglecting the physical activity, physical movement where television, video games, series and lots gadgets covers the children space where they are not much involved in spending time in play , learn , progress in a environment surrounding which may lead to the lack of functional movements , creativity of thinking , cognitive thinking etc. Same as similar happens on the most of the women life style electronic gadgets play an important role in the daily life style as for each and every thing the usage of machinery plays vital role which make a less workable physically and also the connection with the natural things to be done manually, as it may lead to the spiritual , emotional, self thinking, cognitive thinking, physical health to be drag down so that knowing and aware by self through the knowledge of the holistic education , holistic health and physical activity will be change full of negative and draw back of health consciousness. As women are the care taker in majority of the family, they may initiate the family members and also develop the children health and the value of holistic development, education, health, physical education , physical activity etc. Holistic education is approach to teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. School physical education represents a context that has the potential for promoting positive growth development by helping students acquire life skills and psychosocial and behavioural attributes that can transfer to other important domains in the area of school, family members , work station , concurrently and over the life time span.

A Healthy Relationship between Student -Teacher through Holistic Education

The Healthy Student and Teacher Relationships is a must factor which cant be avoided as each and every school going child must face the teacher ,since while teachers are able to form strong connective bonds with children(students), the children performance in class and engagement is positive. Child may have a higher chance of success in a learning environment. Teachers is the ladder of the students' strengths and needs. Teachers encouragement, trust and communication among the holistic education and health will make students to increases their motivation to do well and to be developed in the holistic area of health and education through physical education. In this aspect teachers must also be equip in knowing importance of holistic education, holistic health and physical education (physical activity)

Holistic Health Inter- related with Physical Education among Children

Many consider physical education to be more than physical activity, it is an academic discipline, and should include motor learning, sport skills, social development, and other behavioural building aspects. It is vital to develop and in still positive attitude towards physical activities to enhance children health. Though, holistic health is inter related with the benefits of physical activity doing benefits because doing physical activity full fill the various dimension health which is present in holistic health. Thus, physical education ensures optimal health and focuses on an early lifestyle of healthy living and well being which persist through childhood and adolescence. The education system along with the policy makers can bring about the change associated with both physiological and psychological variables.

Benefits of Physical Education; Which mostly fulfil the aspects of Holistic dimension Criteria

- 1) Enhances the learning aptitude of the children
- 2) Improves cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, flexibility, mobility, and body consumption of the children.
- 3) Helps in improving power, agility, reaction, time, balance, speed, and coordination by use of all senses.
- 4) Develops interpersonal skills of the children like teamwork, leadership, communication, etc.
- 5) Helps the children to combat the mental health issues like stress and anxiety.
- 6) Helps to build resilience and emotional stability.

The Need and Importance of Holistic Health among Women

Some of the authors claim that the nature of woman is "spiritual and expansive" where as man is "more physical, condensed and active". Others believe that "all women have an intuitive understanding of Infinity, especially when they bear children". Within the feminist discourse there tends to be two streams: the one view which believes that women's spiritual superiority over men is mostly due to biological factors and the other view which believes that differences between women and men are best explained by different socio-cultural experiences.

Conclusion

“wholeness” is the core of the educational process ,Wholeness implies that each academic discipline provides merely a different perspective on the rich, complex, integrated phenomenon of life. Holistic education celebrates and makes constructive use of evolving, alternate views of reality and multiple ways of knowing. It is not only the intellectual and vocational aspects of human development that need guidance and nurturance, but also the physical, social, moral, aesthetic, creative, and — in a non-sectarian sense — spiritual aspects. Since, these days we all are very much aware of the health, well being even though we are not making sure that we full fil our health aspect and not conscious whether we are involving in physical activity and following the healthy life style. Though a holistic education we can know the importance of healthy and its dimension value like, social emotional, physical, cognitive thinking, self-help, fine motor, cross motor ,spiritual etc. While the teacher have the knowledge of it they implies in their classroom teaching, curriculum also practically, then the students will be effectively follow the things with interest class, as when we jump into the women, they may train their child, family and guide them with the knowledge ,values of holistic health and its benefits.

Reference

- [1] Giancarlo Condello (2021) Fostering Holistic Development with a Designed Multisport Intervention in Physical Education: A Class-Randomized Cross-Over Trial, article in World Journal of Environmental Research
- [2] Liebert, M. (2010,).Journal of Metabolic Syndrome and Related Disorders. Pg 1-2. Life Positive, A Complete Guide to Holistic Living. www.lifepositive.com
- [3] Kaladevi P. (2022). Holistic Development of Education Article
- [4] Edward T. (1998). Guideline for designing a holistic school.

ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Nowadays, advances in technology play a significant role not only in human life but also in the field of education. The growing popularity and use of social media have influenced every facets of life. Social media has great impact on the education sector especially due to pandemic which has pushed all the schools and colleges to take their tutoring online. Students use social media to communicate with their friends and family. It allows them to convey their ideas by posting photographs, articles and videos. The use of social media in education helps students, teachers and parents to get more useful information, to connect with learning groups and other educational systems that make education convenient. Social media makes the teachers more active, flexible, effective and student- centred to sharpen the critical skills among the students. This paper aims to explore the important social media applications and their role in education.

Keywords: *Social Media, Education, Technology, Teaching, Learning.*

Introduction

Technology has influenced almost all facets of our lives and education is not an exception. It has revolutionised the traditional methods of teaching by introducing modern and innovative technologies. With continuing popularity and growth of social media, many educators considering the potential of using social media for educational purposes as they are of the view that social media has the ability to encourage active learning and collaboration among students (Maloney, 2007). Social network tools afford students and institutions with multiple opportunities to increase learning methods. Social media helps students to broaden their perspective on various subjects, enables them to do social learning and contact their peers across the globe. It has been instrumental in assisting them to come closer and share relevant knowledge and information. With the help of social media, students and teachers can improve the technological access and involvement in studies increases because of these latest technologies. Information sharing becomes very easy with the help of internet and social media. Students can connect their friends and teachers through various means of communication such as mobile phones, laptops and personal computers.

Literature Review

Social media has become irreplaceable part of our lives. Human beings of any age or status use social media as it is one of the most useful online platforms. It is an essential form of knowledge along with the stream of fun and it plays a vital role in today's scenario. Development in the field of internet and advent of network technology in communication have given rise to use of social media all over the world. Safko (2009) considers social media as "user-generated content: blogs, audios, videos, music, news, photos, tweets - working together with digital technology in an environment where everything is accessible from everywhere and everything is connected". Liu (2010) emphasises that leachers need to be careful while incorporating technology in teaching and proper implementation strategies are required to employ social media in classrooms. The purpose of utilizing social media tools in language classroom is to improve teaching and learning and if not used properly it can distract students from learning to other activities. The Integration of social media the latest medium that is used as an innovative way to delegate education purposes. Social media is an interactive platform where users are able to generate contents based on mobile and webs technologies for multiple sharing activities. Social media has a crucial impact where it is strictly based on web-based and it is a free, supportive and interactive enhancer for developing pupils' learning experiences in providing network opportunities (Roopchund, Ramesh & Janky, 2018). Recent studies reveal that technology assisted instruction is more effective than traditional methods to help teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning. Tiene (2000) found that written communication using social media allows students to actively participate in discussion at a convenient time and also facilitates them to express themselves in a more clearer, planned and structured way.

Role of Social Media in Education

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Social media refers to the social software in the form of websites and other online groups such as social networking and microblogging to share conversations, personal messages, ideas information or to grow social and professional contacts. There are various kinds of social media which may be used in several ways. Some of the most commonly used social media are Blogs, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, Whatsapp, Instagram, Telegram etc.

Blogs: Blogs can be used by the teachers as well as the students to write things range from news and their perceptions on some specific issues. They invite the readers to reply by adding or posting comments on their blogs. Blogs assist the users in improving the reading speed, vocabularies and promote proper use of grammar and enhanced reading comprehension of the learners. Blogs are used to capture real-world writing experiences and class blogs can be organised to facilitate easy learning. Teachers can also update information meant for student, relating to assignment and homework. They can provide feedback suggestions and comments in blogs to encourage to help each other with their writing. Students can also comment on each other's work, thus building peer networks which, in turn, develop their knowledge.

Facebook: Blattner. & Fiori (2009) stated that Facebook is primary social network that takes pride in its more than billions followers and it is one of the fastest growing and well known sites on the internet. Facebook has various tasks of communications, material sharing, modification and collaborative construction. However the main reason for students to use Facebook is to contact with friends. Teachers can create Facebook group and use it to remind students of upcoming assignments, share links to helpful websites and upload documents. Students can post questions about homework, opinions on a class reading, and share concerns about the class in a way that they may not feel comfortable in other sittings.

Twitter: Twitter can be used by the students to share their opinions about topics, in the classroom and start a discussion. They can share pictures to further emphasise their ideas as well as read updates from celebrities. The character limit of Twitter encourages succinct and clear writing for the students. Twitter is a platform that allows users to write brief text updates. In the context of education, pedagogical tweeting represents a proficient and natural way through which teachers can identify students' thoughts hence making learning more meaningful, fun, enjoyable and effective (Menkhoff et al.,2015). Teachers have to propose alternative activities that reinforce students' knowledge. Twitter allows posting online writing activities without the necessity to have the teacher physically to hand their homework or any assignment. Since the internet contains an infinite supply of information that can be shared with students easily by using a hashtag and tagging the students via Twitter, they can access this online repository immediately.

You Tube: You Tube is a video sharing website that provides good quality education that has been developed a lot during the past few years. By using YouTube, a student from one country can have access to education from another country. Teachers can provide quality education which is not able to reach many students in a traditional way. Students give much more attention to the videos than those in the traditional teaching environment. This makes learning comfortable and easy. Teachers can provide quality teaching to students with the help of YouTube. They can upload videos of their lectures so that their students can clarify doubts online. This makes it easy for the students to view through their tablets or mobile phones. YouTube can be used for sharing online videos, creating and sharing presentations, and getting learners to take part actively by asking them to comment.

WhatsApp: WhatsApp is used as a communication, collaborative and transactional tool in the teaching and learning process. WhatsApp in education helps to democratise learning and empower educators and educational institutions to disseminate knowledge and skills to more learners. It supports free voice and video calls so teachers and students can stay in touch, even outside stipulated study periods. Teachers can send timely reminders or notifications about exams, homework due dates, etc. to keep students engaged with learning material and the subject. In addition to offering a highly accessible, easy to use, and low - and low connectivity platform for teachers, WhatsApp is also an excellent tool for community-based learning. Teachers can leverage WhatsApp for online teaching to deliver lectures in a virtual environment. They can provide videos, audio-clips, PPTs, notes and other resources to ensure that students continue to learn, even outside the physical boundaries of the traditional classroom. Students can also use WhatsApp for educational purposes- to learn remotely, to connect with teachers and classmates, and enhance their knowledge and skills.

Advantage of Social Media

Social media engages the students and encourages them to express themselves. It enhances students collaboration. They can easily interact and share information, work together on projects and communicate freely and easily. Social media allows the teachers to share resources like images, videos, worksheets and websites effortlessly and effectively. Teachers may reach out to parents with comments, feedback and suggestions. Social

media improves the chance to learn by enabling students and teachers to link and communicate in new interesting ways. It helps to increase communication skills and provide a back door' for shy learners. It provides an outlet for students who are to a intimidated to raise their hands in class. Online discussion forums increases students' critical thinking skills. They can get better media and information technology skills when social media is used actively in class and students get prepared for the contemporary society that is permeated by digital media.

Conclusion

Today, teaching and learning requires much more space, time, personal and group flexibility, less fixed content and more open research and communication processes. The teachers should explore new and creative strategies to employ educational innovation for future learning. The students welcome the use of the social networking sites as supplementary to the curriculum and most of them love spending time on them. Videos and other sharing activities are useful for them. Thus social media plays an important role in providing choices, and opportunities for the students to take control of their learning. These kinds of opportunities and environments create conditions for the facilitation and development of learners autonomy.

References

- [1] Blattner, Geraldine and Fiori, Melissa. "Facebook in the Language Classroom
- [2] Promises and Possibilities". *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning* 6(1), 2009.
- [3] Krishen, S.D. *Principles and Practices in Second Language Acquisition*. Oxford: Pergamon Press Inc, 1981.
- [4] Liu, Y. "Social Media Tools as a Learning Resource".
- [5] *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*. 3(1), 2010.
- [6] Maloney, E. *What Web 2.0 can Teach Us about Learning?* *Chronicles of Higher Education*, 2007.
- [7] Menkhoff, T., Chay, Y.W., Bengtsson, M.L., Woodard, C.J., and Gan, B.
- [8] "Incorporating Microblogging ("tweeting") in Higher Education: Lessons Learnt in a Knowledge Management Course". *Computer in Human Behaviour*, 2015.
- [9] Roopchand, R. Ramesh, V. And Janky, R. "Use of Social Media for Improving Student Engagement at Universite des Mascareignes (UDM)". *Proceedings of Fifth International Conference, India*. Vol. 2, 2018.
- [10] Safko, L and Brake, K.D. *The Social Media Bible: Tactics, Tools, and Strategies for Business Success*. Hoboken, N.J.: John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [11] <https://www.gupshup.io/resources/blog/whatsapp-for-education-a-complete-guide>. Web
- [12]

READINESS FOR ONLINE SYNCHRONOUS SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT: AN EXPLORATION DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHER EDUCATION IN SRI LANKA

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The Covid-19 pandemic crisis had a direct impact on the education systems throughout the world that had not been previously imagined. Sri Lankan higher education authorities were also compelled to transfer from traditional methods of teaching, learning, and assessment to online digital modalities. Except for the distance education modality of teacher education all other teacher education programs in Sri Lanka were implemented in face-to-face onsite teaching and learning for many decades. The Faculty of Education, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka which adopted onsite teaching-learning systems had to comply with the need for online teaching for the first time in its history of more than 50 years. The implementation of teaching and learning online was possible due to the Information Communication Technology curriculum included in the teacher education programs to empower the trainees. The online teaching-learning was done satisfactorily during the Covid-19 pandemic to fulfill student learning needs. The teaching-learning was although mainly synchronous, the opportunity for asynchronous learning using the material uploaded to the Learning Management System (LMS) was made available. However, the online assessment was an issue that needed negotiation with the students.

During Covid-19 when the pandemic was continuing there was no option to postpone examinations indefinitely and the faculty came to a decision to conduct summative assessments online. Online assessments were done adopting somewhat a similar strategy to onsite assessments. The online assessments were planned to be conducted as a synchronous summative assessment. The students were grouped and each small group was assigned to an academic who would supervise the examination process. The question papers were uploaded to the LMS one hour before the scheduled time for the onset of the examination to prevent any issues of accessing the examination paper due to weak internet services in various parts of the country. A reasonable time extension was allocated to students for uploading the scanned answer scripts to LMS. The main objective of this empirical study was to explore the perceptions of readiness toward online synchronous assessment of Bachelor of Education (BEd) undergraduates who are pre-service teacher trainees. BEd at the University of Colombo is a four-year degree program introduced five decades ago.

The mixed methods design was adopted for the study. The sample was drawn from all the undergraduates of the Bachelor of Education program using a stratified random sampling method. The data were collected using an online survey administering a structured questionnaire distributed to 140 BEd undergraduates. Telephone interviews were conducted with twenty-five students. Each statement in the questionnaire was to be rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from totally agree to totally disagree. Descriptive methods were used to analyze the data. The findings reveal that the majority (63.3%) of students participated in online learning using their smartphones. 55% of students used the smartphone as the only device to connect to the internet. According to the year of study, B.Ed final year students (61.5%) were more positively inclined toward online synchronous summative assessments than the students in the initial years of the BEd program. The readiness for online synchronous summative assessments was low (11.6%) in Tamil medium students. The majority of Sinhala (62.8%) and English medium (61.1%) students preferred to take their summative assessment as online asynchronous assignments while Tamil medium (50.7%) students opted for traditional onsite classroom examinations. The findings showed that the readiness for synchronous online assessment is low among the BEd teacher trainees. When probed through interviews the trainees expressed the reasons for their reluctance for online assessments, especially for online summative assessments. However, all teacher trainees accepted the need for adaptation to alternative online methods of assessments during the Covid-19 pandemic and in similar future uncertainties and expressed that they were ready and flexible to adopt new assessment approaches if the issues of resources can be minimized. Towards this effort, Sri Lanka's teacher educator capacity development for online synchronous assessments should be introduced harnessing the expertise of local and international resource persons. More investment in terms of student support would be needed if online learning is to be promoted more widely and equitably among teacher trainee undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Bachelor of Education, Pre-Service Teacher Trainees, Online Assessment

DIFFERENT TYPES OF TRANSLATION IN BIPOLAR VALUED MULTI I-FUZZY NORMAL SUBRINGS OF A RING

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Abstract

In this paper, different types of translation in bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy normal subring of a ring are defined and studied; translations are used in applications and some translation theorems are introduced.

Keywords: Interval valued fuzzy subset, bipolar valued fuzzy subset, bipolar valued multi fuzzy subset, bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy subset, bipolar valued multi fuzzy subring, bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy subring, bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy normal subring and translations.

Introduction

In 1965, Zadeh [16] introduced the notion of a fuzzy subset of a set, fuzzy sets are a kind of useful mathematical structure to represent a collection of objects whose boundary is vague. Since then it has become a vigorous area of research in different domains, there have been a number of generalizations of this fundamental concept such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets, interval-valued fuzzy sets, vague sets, soft sets etc. Fuzzy group was introduced by Azriel Rosenfeld [4]. After that Fuzzy groups Redefined was introduced by Anthony.J.M and H.Sherwood[2] and Q-fuzzy concepts were applied in nearring by Chitra.V and K.Arjunan[6]. Multi fuzzy sets was introduced by Sabu Sebastian, T.V.Ramakrishnan[12]. Lee [9] introduced the notion of bipolar valued fuzzy sets. Bipolar valued fuzzy sets are an extension of fuzzy sets whose membership degree range is enlarged from the interval $[0, 1]$ to $[-1, 1]$. Bipolar valued fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets look similar each other. However, they are different each other [9, 10]. After that bipolar valued fuzzy subgroups of a group was introduced by Anitha.M.S et al [1] and Arsham Borumand Saeid[3] introduced the bipolar valued fuzzy BCK/BCI-algebras. Properties of Bipolar interval valued fuzzy subgroups of a group were introduced by Balasubramanian.A et al [5]. Bipolar fuzzy subalgebras and bipolar fuzzy ideals of BCK/BCI-algebras were introduced by Kyoung Ja Lee[8]. A study on interval valued fuzzy subsemirings of a semiring was introduced by Murugalingam.K and K.Arjunan[11] and Shanmugapriya.M.M & K.Arjunan[13] introduced the (Q, L) -Fuzzy subnearrings of a nearring. "A study on interval valued fuzzy, anti fuzzy, intuitionistic fuzzy subrings of a ring" by Somasundra Moorthy.M.G[14], the thesis was useful for writing this paper. In this paper, the concept of translations in bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy subring of a ring is introduced and established some results.

1.Preliminaries

Definition 1.1. [16] Let X be any nonempty set. A mapping $[M] : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is called an interval valued fuzzy subset (briefly, I-FS) of X , where $D[0,1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ and $[M](x) = [M^-(x), M^+(x)]$, for all x in X , where M^- and M^+ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $M^-(x) \leq M^+(x)$, for all x in X . Thus $[M](x)$ is an interval (a closed subset of $[0, 1]$) and not a number from the interval $[0, 1]$ as in the case of fuzzy subset. Note that $[0] = [0, 0]$ and $[1] = [1, 1]$.

Definition 1.2. [9] A bipolar valued fuzzy set (BVFS) D in X is defined as an object of the form $D = \{ \langle x, D^+(x), D^-(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$, where $D^+ : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $D^- : X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$. The positive membership degree $D^+(x)$ denotes the satisfaction degree of an element x to the property corresponding to a bipolar valued fuzzy set D and the negative membership degree $D^-(x)$ denotes the satisfaction degree of an element x to some implicit counter-property corresponding to a bipolar valued fuzzy set D .

Example 1.3. $A = \{ \langle x, 0.5, -0.6 \rangle, \langle y, 0.3, -0.9 \rangle, \langle z, 0.8, -0.4 \rangle \}$ is a BVFS of $X = \{ u, v, w \}$.

Definition 1.4. [15] A bipolar valued multi fuzzy set (BVMFS) A in X is defined as an object of the form $A = \{ \langle x, A_1^+(x), A_2^+(x), \dots, A_n^+(x), A_1^-(x), A_2^-(x), \dots, A_n^-(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$, where $A_i^+ : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $A_i^- : X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$, for all i . The positive membership degrees $A_i^+(x)$ denote the satisfaction degree of an element x to the property corresponding to a bipolar valued multi fuzzy set A and the negative membership degrees $A_i^-(x)$ denote the satisfaction degree of an element x to some implicit counter-property corresponding to a bipolar valued multi

fuzzy set A.

Example 1.5. $C = \{ \langle u, 0.3, 0.7, 0.4, -0.9, -0.5, -0.4 \rangle, \langle v, 0.6, 0.4, 0.8, -0.5, -0.7, -0.2 \rangle, \langle w, 0.3, 0.9, 0.7, -0.2, -0.4, -0.6 \rangle \}$ is a BVMFS of $X = \{ u, v, w \}$.

Definition 1.6 A bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy set (BVMI-FS) A in X is defined as an object of the form $[A] = \{ \langle x, [A]_1^+(x), [A]_2^+(x), \dots, [A]_n^+(x), [A]_1^-(x), [A]_2^-(x), \dots, [A]_n^-(x) \rangle / x \in X \}$, where $[A]_i^+ : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ and $[A]_i^- : X \rightarrow D[-1, 0]$, for all i, where $D[0,1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[0, 1]$ and $D[-1, 0]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of $[-1, 0]$. The positive membership degrees interval $[A]_i^+(x)$ denote the satisfaction degree interval of an element x to the property corresponding to a bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy set [A] and the negative membership degrees interval $[A]_i^-(x)$ denote the satisfaction degree interval of an element x to some implicit counter-property corresponding to a bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy set [A]. Note that $[0] = [0, 0]$, $[1] = [1, 1]$ and $[-1] = [-1, -1]$.

Example 1.7. $A = \{ \langle x, [0.4, 0.5], [0.6, 0.7], [0.1, 0.3], [-0.8, -0.7], [-0.7, -0.5], [-0.5, -0.2] \rangle, \langle y, [0.7, 0.8], [0.4, 0.5], [0.6, 0.9], [-0.5, -0.3], [-0.7, -0.5], [-1, -0.8] \rangle, \langle z, [0.3, 0.6], [0.7, 0.9], [0.7, 1], [-0.8, -0.4], [-0.9, -0.5], [-0.6, -0.1] \rangle \}$ is a BVMI-FS of $X = \{ x, y, z \}$.

Definition 1.8. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. A BVMFS B of R is said to be a bipolar valued multi fuzzy subring of R (BVMFSR) if the following conditions are satisfied, for all i,

- (i) $B_i^+(u-v) \geq \min\{ B_i^+(u), B_i^+(v) \}$
- (ii) $B_i^+(uv) \geq \min\{ B_i^+(u), B_i^+(v) \}$
- (iii) $B_i^-(u-v) \leq \max\{ B_i^-(u), B_i^-(v) \}$
- (iv) $B_i^-(uv) \leq \max\{ B_i^-(u), B_i^-(v) \}, \forall u, v \in R$.

Definition 1.9. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. A BVMI-FS [B] of R is said to be a bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy subring of R (BVMI-FSR) if the following conditions are satisfied, for all i,

- (i) $[B]_i^+(u-v) \geq \text{rmin}\{ [B]_i^+(u), [B]_i^+(v) \}$
- (ii) $[B]_i^+(uv) \geq \text{rmin}\{ [B]_i^+(u), [B]_i^+(v) \}$
- (iii) $[B]_i^-(u-v) \leq \text{rmax}\{ [B]_i^-(u), [B]_i^-(v) \}$
- (iv) $[B]_i^-(uv) \leq \text{rmax}\{ [B]_i^-(u), [B]_i^-(v) \}, \forall u, v \in R$, where $\text{rmin}\{ [a, b], [c, d] \} = [\min\{ a, c \}, \min\{ b, d \}]$ and $\text{rmax}\{ [a, b], [c, d] \} = [\max\{ a, c \}, \max\{ b, d \}]$.

Example 1.10. Let $R = Z_3 = \{ 0, 1, 2 \}$ be a ring with respect to addition modulo 3 and multiplication modulo 3. Then $[A] = \{ \langle 0, [0.72, 0.81], [0.91, 1], [0.52, 0.63], [-0.91, -0.81], [-1, -0.91], [-0.81, -0.72] \rangle, \langle 1, [0.51, 0.61], [0.71, 0.81], [0.31, 0.41], [-0.71, -0.61], [-0.61, -0.51], [-0.51, -0.41] \rangle, \langle 2, [0.51, 0.61], [0.71, 0.81], [0.31, 0.41], [-0.71, -0.61], [-0.61, -0.51], [-0.51, -0.41] \rangle \}$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R.

Definition 1.11. Let $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a ring. A BVMI-FSR [B] of R is said to be a bipolar valued multi I-fuzzy normal subring of R (BVMI-FNSR) if the following conditions are satisfied, for all i,

- (i) $[B]_i^+(uv) = [B]_i^+(vu)$,
- (ii) $[B]_i^-(uv) = [B]_i^-(vu), \forall u, v \in R$.

Definition 1.12. Let $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ be a BVMI-FS of X. Then the following translations are defined as

(i) $?([A]) = \langle ?[A]_1^+, ?[A]_2^+, \dots, ?[A]_n^+, ?[A]_1^-, ?[A]_2^-, \dots, ?[A]_n^- \rangle$, where $?[A]_i^+(x) = \text{rmin}\{ [1/2, 1/2], [A]_i^+(x) \}$ and $?[A]_i^-(x) = \text{rmax}\{ [-1/2, -1/2], [A]_i^-(x) \}$, for all x in X and for all i.

(ii) $!([A]) = \langle ![A]_1^+, ![A]_2^+, \dots, ![A]_n^+, ![A]_1^-, ![A]_2^-, \dots, ![A]_n^- \rangle$, where $![A]_i^+(x) = \text{rmax}\{ [1/2, 1/2], [A]_i^+(x) \}$ and $![A]_i^-(x) = \text{rmin}\{ [-1/2, -1/2], [A]_i^-(x) \}$, for all x in X.

(iii) $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]) = \langle Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^+), Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^+), \dots, Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^+), Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^-), Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^-), \dots, Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^-) \rangle$, where $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(x)) = \text{rmin}\{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(x) \}$ and $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(x)) = \text{rmax}\{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(x) \}$, for all x in X and α_i in $D[0, 1]$ and β_i in $D[-1, 0]$ and for all i.

(iv) $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]) = \langle P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^+), P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^+), \dots, P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^+), P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^-), P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^-), \dots, P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^-) \rangle$, where $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(x)) = \text{rmax}\{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(x) \}$ and $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(x)) = \text{rmin}\{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(x) \}$, for all x in X and α_i in $D[0, 1]$ and β_i in $D[-1, 0]$ and for all i.

(v) $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]) = \langle G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^+), G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^+), \dots, G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^+), G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_1^-), G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_2^-), \dots, G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_n^-) \rangle$, where $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(x)) = \alpha_i [A]_i^+(x)$ and $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(x)) = -\beta_i [A]_i^-(x)$, for all x in X and α_i in $[0, 1]$ and β_i in $[-1, 0]$ and for all i.

Theorem 1.13. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ and $[B] = \langle [B]_1^+, [B]_2^+, \dots, [B]_n^+, [B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$

$[B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$ are two BVMI-FNSRs of a ring R , then their intersection $A \cap B$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

2. Some Theorems

Theorem 2.1. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FSR of a ring R , then $?([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

Theorem 2.2. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $?([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. For every x, y in R , for all i ,
 by Theorem 2.1, $?[A]$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .
 And $?[A]_i^+(xy) = \text{rmin} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmin} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(yx) \}$
 $= ?[A]_i^+(yx)$, for all x, y in R .
 Also $?[A]_i^-(xy) = \text{rmax} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmax} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(yx) \}$
 $= ?[A]_i^-(yx)$, for all x and y in R .

Hence $?[A]$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Theorem 2.3. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FSR of a ring R , then $!([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

Theorem 2.4. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $!([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. For every x, y in R , for all i ,
 by Theorem 2.3, $!([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .
 And $![A]_i^+(xy) = \text{rmax} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmax} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(yx) \}$
 $= ![A]_i^+(yx)$, for all x and y in R .
 Also $![A]_i^-(xy) = \text{rmin} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmin} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(yx) \}$
 $= ![A]_i^-(yx)$, for all x and y in R .

Hence $![A]$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Theorem 2.5. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FSR of a ring R , then $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

Theorem 2.6. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. For every x, y in R , α_i in $D[0, 1]$, β_i in $D[-1, 0]$ and for all i ,
 by Theorem 2.5, $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .
 And $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(xy)) = \text{rmin} \{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmin} \{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(yx) \}$
 $= Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(yx))$, for all x, y in R .
 Also $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(xy)) = \text{rmax} \{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmax} \{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(yx) \}$
 $= Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(yx))$, for all x, y in R .

Hence $Q_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Theorem 2.7. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FSR of a ring R , then $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

Theorem 2.8. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. For every x, y in R , α_i in $D[0, 1]$, β_i in $D[-1, 0]$ and for all i ,
 by Theorem 2.7, $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .
 And $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(xy)) = \text{rmax} \{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmax} \{ \alpha_i, [A]_i^+(yx) \}$
 $= P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(yx))$, for all x, y in R .
 Also $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(xy)) = \text{rmin} \{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(xy) \}$
 $= \text{rmin} \{ \beta_i, [A]_i^-(yx) \}$

$$= P_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(yx)), \text{ for all } x, y \text{ in } R.$$

Hence $P_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Theorem 2.9. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FSR of a ring R , then $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

Theorem 2.10. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. For every x, y in R , α_i in $D[0, 1]$, β_i in $D[-1, 0]$ and for all i ,

By Theorem 2.10, $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FSR of R .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(xy)) &= \alpha_i [A]_i^+(xy) \\ &= \alpha_i [A]_i^+(yx) \\ &= G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^+(yx)), \text{ for all } x, y \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also } G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(xy)) &= -\beta_i [A]_i^-(xy) \\ &= -\beta_i [A]_i^-(yx) \\ &= G_{\alpha, \beta}([A]_i^-(yx)), \text{ for all } x, y \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $G_{\alpha, \beta}([A])$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Theorem 2.11. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ and $[B] = \langle [B]_1^+, [B]_2^+, \dots, [B]_n^+, [B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$ are BVMI-FSs of a ring R , then $!([A] \cap [B]) = !([A]) \cap !([B])$.

Proof. For every x in R , for all i ,

$$\begin{aligned} !([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x) &= rmax \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], ([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x) \} \\ &= rmax \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], rmin \{ [A]_i^+(x), [B]_i^+(x) \} \} \\ &= rmin \{ rmax \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(x) \}, rmax \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [B]_i^+(x) \} \} \\ &= rmin \{ ![A]_i^+(x), ![B]_i^+(x) \} \\ &= !([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x), \text{ for all } x \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } !([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x) &= rmin \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], ([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x) \} \\ &= rmin \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], rmax \{ [A]_i^-(x), [B]_i^-(x) \} \} \\ &= rmax \{ rmin \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(x) \}, rmin \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [B]_i^-(x) \} \} \\ &= rmax \{ ![A]_i^-(x), ![B]_i^-(x) \} \\ &= !([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x), \text{ for all } x \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $!([A] \cap [B]) = !([A]) \cap !([B])$.

Theorem 2.12. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ and $[B] = \langle [B]_1^+, [B]_2^+, \dots, [B]_n^+, [B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$ are BVMI-FNSRs of a ring R , then $!([A] \cap [B]) = !([A]) \cap !([B])$ is also a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. The proof follows from the Theorems 1.13, 2.4 and 2.11.

Theorem 2.13. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ and $[B] = \langle [B]_1^+, [B]_2^+, \dots, [B]_n^+, [B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$ are BVMI-FSs of a ring R , then $?([A] \cap [B]) = ?([A]) \cap ?([B])$.

Proof. For every x in R , for all i ,

$$\begin{aligned} ?([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x) &= rmin \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], ([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x) \} \\ &= rmin \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], rmin \{ [A]_i^+(x), [B]_i^+(x) \} \} \\ &= rmin \{ rmin \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(x) \}, rmin \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [B]_i^+(x) \} \} \\ &= rmin \{ ?[A]_i^+(x), ?[B]_i^+(x) \} \\ &= ?([A]_i^+ \cap [B]_i^+)(x), \text{ for all } x \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } ?([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x) &= rmax \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], ([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x) \} \\ &= rmax \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], rmax \{ [A]_i^-(x), [B]_i^-(x) \} \} \\ &= rmax \{ rmax \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(x) \}, rmax \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [B]_i^-(x) \} \} \\ &= rmax \{ ?[A]_i^-(x), ?[B]_i^-(x) \} \\ &= ?([A]_i^- \cap [B]_i^-)(x), \text{ for all } x \text{ in } R. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $?([A] \cap [B]) = ?([A]) \cap ?([B])$.

Theorem 2.14. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ and $[B] = \langle [B]_1^+, [B]_2^+, \dots, [B]_n^+, [B]_1^-, [B]_2^-, \dots, [B]_n^- \rangle$ are BVMI-FNSRs of a ring R , then $?([A] \cap [B]) = ?([A]) \cap ?([B])$ is also a BVMI-FNSR of R .

Proof. The proof follows from the Theorems 1.13, 2.2 and 2.13.

Theorem 2.15. If $[A] = \langle [A]_1^+, [A]_2^+, \dots, [A]_n^+, [A]_1^-, [A]_2^-, \dots, [A]_n^- \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of a ring R , then $!(?(A)) = ?(!A) = \langle [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], \dots, [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], \dots, [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}] \rangle$ is also a constant

BVMI-FNSR of R.

Proof. For every x in R and for all i ,

$?[A]_i^+(x) = \text{rmin} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(x) \} \leq [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}]$ and $![A]_i^+(x) = \text{rmax} \{ [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^+(x) \} \geq [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}]$,
so $!(?[A]_i^+) = ?(![A]_i^+) = [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}]$.

And $?[A]_i^-(x) = \text{rmax} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(x) \} \geq [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}]$ and $![A]_i^-(x) = \text{rmin} \{ [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [A]_i^-(x) \} \leq [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}]$, so $!(?[A]_i^-) = ?(![A]_i^-) = [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}]$.

Hence $!(?[A]) = ?(![A]) = \langle [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], \dots, [\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}], [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}], \dots, [-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}] \rangle$ is a BVMI-FNSR of R.

References

- [1] Anitha.M.S., Muruganantha Prasad & K.Arjunan, "Notes on Bipolar-valued fuzzy subgroups of a group", *Bulletin of Society for Mathematical Services and Standards*, Vol. 2 No. 3 (2013), pp. 52 – 59.
- [2] Anthony.J.M and H.Sherwood, "Fuzzy groups Redefined", *Journal of mathematical analysis and applications*, 69(1979), 124 –130.
- [3] Arsham Borumand Saeid, "Bipolar-valued fuzzy BCK/BCI-algebras", *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 7 (11) (2009), 1404 – 1411.
- [4] Azriel Rosenfeld, "Fuzzy groups", *Journal of mathematical analysis and applications*, 35(1971), 512 – 517.
- [5] Balasubramanian.A, K.L.Muruganantha Prasad & K.Arjunan, "Properties of Bipolar interval valued fuzzy subgroups of a group", *International Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol. 4, Iss. 4 (2015), 262 - 268.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

INNOVATIVE TEACHING THROUGH COMIC STRIPS FOR HOLISTIC LEARNING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This study wants to explore the effect and challenge of using comic strips in Innovative teaching English and holistic approach for language learning. A comic strip is a sequence of drawings, often cartoons, arranged in interrelated panels to display brief humor or form a narrative, often serialized, with text in balloons and captions. Traditionally, throughout the 20th and 21st century, these have been published in newspapers and magazines, with daily horizontal strips printed in black-and-white in newspapers, while Sunday papers offered longer sequences in special color comics sections. With the advent of the internet, online comic strips began to appear as web comics. This thematic paper highlights the importance of comic strips as innovative teaching approach in English language learning.

Introduction

Teaching is the process of heeding people's needs, experiences, and feelings and inquisitive so that they learn specific things. In major function of education is to make learning beneficial and meaningful and also this process aims at the transmission of knowledge, and imparting skills, values and behavior. Teaching is defined as a process which students are prepared for learning by providing initial structure to clarify planned outcomes and indicate derived learning activities productively. Such teaching should be carried out with innovative approach so that learning process can attain the planned outcomes.

Innovative Teaching

Teaching is one of the determining jobs which make an enormous role in the life of every person. Renewing traditional methods to make learning easier for students is their focus. To do that innovative teaching method is the new way of teaching. This would include creativity, collaboration, communication & connectivity in teaching methods. A great poet William butler Yeats once said: "Education should not be the filling of a pail, but the lightening of a fire". The use of innovative teaching methods better assist students and teach them to benefits out of innovative thinking and does more than "fill the pail. "It helps to kindle the passion for learning also provides students the necessary tools to succeed in the 21st century. The innovation in teaching can improve teaching learning process such as

- 1) Involves creativity and makes learning interesting.
- 2) Through innovative technology methods children can explore the world and fulfill their curiosity.
- 3) Innovative learning is more engrossing through technology as keeps the children focused versus in the classroom where they may be distracted.
- 4) Makes collaboration easier as students, teachers and parents can communicate effectively.
- 5) Students learn early on as they build technology based skills.
- 6) Reduces the needs of textbooks thus lowering costs incurred by students and schools.
- 7) Faster and more effective delivery of lessons.
- 8) STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Math) helps to prepare students for the future by entitling them with skills they would need to be successful later in life.

English Language

The English Language teaching tradition has been subject to tremendous change, especially throughout the twentieth century. Perhaps more than any other discipline, this tradition has been practiced, in various adaptations, in language classrooms all around the world for centuries. While the teaching of Maths or Physics, that is, the methodology of teaching Math's or Physics, has, to a greater or lesser extent, remained the same, this is hardly the case with English or language teaching in general. As will become evident in this short paper, there are some milestones in the development of this tradition, which we will briefly touch upon, in an attempt to reveal the

importance of research in the selection and implementation of the optimal methods and techniques for language teaching and learning. Nowadays, more and more people are dedicating time in studying English as a second language. Many countries include English in their school syllabus and children start learn English at a younger and younger age. Whether we are looking for a new job or planning to travel the world, studying English can help us progress in life both personally and professionally.

English is a Global Language

English is the most commonly spoken language in the world. One out of five people can speak or at least understand English. English is the language of science, aviation, computers, and tourism. Knowing English increases your chances of getting a good job in a multinational company within your home country or of finding work abroad. English the official language of 53 countries and is used as a lingua franca [a mutually known language] by people from all around the world. This means that whether we're working in Beijing or, travelling in Brazil, studying English can help you have compensation with people from all over the world. Learning English benefit everyone in many ways. In India, English is considered as Second Language. Learning Second Language needs some innovative teaching strategies. Under innovative teaching strategies comic strips plays a vital role.

Comic Strips

A comic strip is sequence of drawings, often cartoons, arranged in interrelated panels to display brief humor or form a narrative, often serialized, with text in balloons and captions. Traditionally throughout the 20th and into the 21st century, these have been published in newspapers and magazines, with daily horizontal strips printed in black and white in newspaper, while Sunday papers offered longer sequence color comics sections. Storytelling using a sequence of pictures has existed through history. One medieval European example in textile from is te Bay ux Tapestry. Printed examples emerged in 19th century Germany and in 18th century England, where some of the first satirical or humorous sequential narrative drawings were produced.

Comic Strips in English Language Learning

Comic strips provide vehicle for learning and practicing the English language. Each strip's three or four panels provide a finite accessible world in which funny, interesting looking characters go about their lines. And students with limier reading or speaking skills are not as overwhelmed in dealing with the size of a comic strip as they may be with a book of many pages. Comic strips also don't require long sentences or paragraphs to communicate a good story. Only a few are needed for the characters to reveal their stories.

Conclusion

As one of the suitable teaching media in today's era, comic strips could be used in language teaching. Several studies proved the effectiveness of using comic strips in language teaching with its benefits and challenges. All of those studies agreed that the use of comic strips in language teaching is beneficial. Using comic strips, the learners could express their ideas in the form of images and learn a language. It also improved the students' language components mastery, such as vocabulary and grammar and their reading and their reading and writing skills. In this case, comic strips to teach vocabulary and grammar could be seen in the process of introducing models and pronouns and changing direct speech into indirect speech in the speech balloon. Comic strip also supports the words or grammar used in the dialogues, making the text more comprehensible for the students as in learning English Language reading and writing skills.

References

- [1] Arikunto Suharsimi (2002) Procedure Penelitian: Sutu Pendekatan Praktek, Jakarta:PT.Rineka Cipta.
- [2] Ary Donald et al (2010). Introduction to Research in Education. (Eight Edition), New York: CBS College publishing.
- [3] Brown H. Douglas (1994) Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach To Language Pedagogy, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall Regents.
- [4] Brown H. Douglas (2000) Teaching by Principles (Second Edition), London: Longman. Csabay, Noemi. Using Comic Strips in Language Classes, *English Teaching Forum Journal* Gene Yang, Comics in Education.

ROLE OF LIBRARY AUTOMATION IN THE MODERNIZATION OF TECHNICAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Computers are become a necessary component of our daily life. One may accomplish a variety of jobs connected to analysis, computation, and publication more effectively with the use of computers. Programs for computers and software assist libraries in addressing the information requirements and demands of patrons. With the introduction of sophisticated library software for automation and digital information preservation, libraries all over the world have changed the services from manual to automate. For reading and reference, a variety of programmes and solutions are accessible. This study aims to gather information and viewpoints on a variety of topics, including automation, computer technology proficiency among library professionals, the profession's educational background and its contribution, tools and technologies utilised by libraries, and key drivers of change, roadblocks, and other impediments that are crucial to automation and skill development. The main goal of higher education is to provide students with specialised and advanced information to become competent and skilled in a variety of human endeavours intended for all societal advancement and the enrichment of human life. Because of the world's reliance on technology, the function of libraries and librarians has evolved recently. The library is regarded as the centre of a university or other higher education facility.

Keywords: *Library Automation, ICT, Educational Institution, AICTE.*

Introduction

The library is an essential part of every educational facility and serves as the centre of teaching and learning activities where students, instructors, and researchers may explore the huge informational resources. In the era of information and communication technology, computers are utilised for routine library maintenance tasks, saving time for both library staff and patrons while also preventing duplication of effort and enhancing the efficiency of the library service. The collection, structure, and services of libraries have undergone a significant transformation in the ICT era. Users' expectations and attitudes have evolved in its sorts at the same time. Additionally, user information-seeking behaviour has evolved significantly.

Significance of Libraries in Technical Education

Every educational institution must have a library. By taking a glance at the library materials available, one may determine the calibre and degree of a Technical Institute. The basic criteria by which one can judge the quality of education in a Technical Institute include the availability of text materials and e-journals in accordance with the AICTE's standards, the system for properly utilising the resources, easy access for users to the library resources, and proper library resource utilisation. A Technical Institute library serves as a hub for research scientists and the students of the faculty there. A library is just as important as a lab for all aspiring engineers. For this reason, not only in the nation but also throughout the entire globe, libraries are renowned as centres for study and development in the fields of science and technology.

Library Automation: Basic Principle and Importance

Library automation is the use of automated equipment and processing methods in libraries. The automation may be used for office tasks, administrative duties, and providing library services to patrons. The employment of computers to carry out typical library housekeeping tasks including acquisition, circulation, cataloguing, reference services, and serial control is known as library automation. Automation is utilised to cut down on staff time spent on monotonous tasks. The use of automated and semiautomatic data processing devices (computers) to carry out customary library housekeeping tasks, such as acquisition, circulation, cataloguing, and reference and serials control, is known as library automation. The phrase "Library Automation" is now by far the most often used to refer to the computer-based automation of library activities. The term "library automation" refers to the employment of automated and semiautomatic data processing tools to carry out typical library tasks including acquisitions, cataloguing, and circulation. Library automation can be separated from similar topics like

information retrieval, automated indexing and abstracting, and automatic textual analysis since these tasks are traditionally associated with libraries even though they are not always carried out in traditional methods. Automation of libraries entails a significant degree of mechanisation of several repetitive and regular operations that were previously completed by people. The amount of human intervention has significantly decreased with the introduction of automation. The automation of libraries has significantly increased since computers first appeared. Along with computer development, communications and audio-visual technologies opened up new information handling options. In contrast to wealthy nations, India only has a few specialised libraries that employ computers. Computers and other semi-automatic tools like punched cards and reprography are used in libraries as part of automation.

Services provided by Automated Library

- 1) References Services
- 2) Current Awareness Services
- 3) Inter Library Loan Services
- 4) Selective Dissemination of Information
- 5) Stock Verification

Objectives of Library Automation

- 1) Create referral centres to manage and assist with catalogue searching, such as the Union catalogue.
- 2) Organize information and document exchanges with other networks.
- 3) Increase the speed of information access.
- 4) Make resource sharing efficient and dependable.
- 5) Implement electronic services and digital operations in libraries.

Library Automation Software

Koha: Koha is made to operate with the least amount of hardware resources possible. It is built in Perl, employs the well-known MySQL open source database management system, and is operated on the Linux operating system in combination with the Apache Web server. With a few more modules, the Koha ILS may also be deployed on Windows operating systems. It is simple to move data from one ILS to Koha. The most recent Koha version, 22.11, which uses AJAX technology and enables Web 2.0 capabilities for social groups in its Web OPAC, is available right now. By visiting a few Koha Web-OPACs of local, national, and worldwide organisations, they have engaged in their research.

Evergreen Software: This Integrated Library System is free and open source (ILS). OPAC, SIP2.0 support for communication with the programme administrator, circulation and cataloguing functions, and search/retrieval are all included.

ABCD Software: English speakers may operate ABCD, which stands for "Automation of libraries and Centers of Documentation." The software suite's goal is clearly expressed in the name, which is to offer automation features not only for conventional libraries but also for other information providers like documentation centres. Using UNESCO's ISIS database technology, it is created by BIREME (WHO, Brazil) in cooperation with the Flemish Interuniversity Council, Belgium.

NewGenLib: Verus Solutions Pvt Ltd. created this comprehensive library management system. Kesavan Institute of Information and Knowledge Management in Hyderabad, India offers domain knowledge.

Alice for Windows: Incorporated library management system Alice for Windows additionally has 10 modules: acquisition, circulation, management, periodicals, journal indexing, multimedia, multilingual, subject authority, web enquiry, book rental, and user self-check. USMARC format is supported by Alice for Windows. On its database, it operates. Therefore, RDBMS is not necessary.

LibSys: Without any prior programming experience, library personnel may immediately begin utilising LibSys due to its ease of use. Due to the little amount of data entry required, the high level of function integration, and the powerful search and query capabilities, it ensures high productivity. LibSys is firmly committed to enhancing goods with reliability and service.

Importance of Library Automation in Professional Education

- 1) Provide users with modern IT-based services such as OPAC and the use of barcode technology.
- 2) Quick information processing and retrieval.
- 3) Competent of dealing with massive amounts of data.
- 4) Time-saving measures for library patrons and staff
- 5) Maintain accurate records.

Conclusion & Recommendation

In order to maximise library efficacy at the lowest possible cost, automation of the library and the usage of open source software are crucial. The workers at the library have less job stress as a result of this approach, which also improves remote and timely delivery of current information to customers. In addition to discussing the qualities of OSS (Open Source Software) that make them suitable for use as efficient library automation software, this article has outlined the key factors that should be taken into account when choosing library software. This article also includes a brief assessment of the various OSS solutions available for integrated library management for the purpose of successfully automating library services using open source software. In an automated library system, the record-keeping procedures and the creation of different reports become relatively simple. However, the effectiveness of any library automation programme depends on how well it is planned and implemented. If libraries adhere to the AICTE standards and make use of all the resources and facilities now available, they may significantly improve the quality of research and instruction at technical institutes.

References

- [1] Chandrakar, K. (2020). Role of library in technical education with reference to Chattisgarh. *International journal of science and research*, 9(2), 250-251.
- [2] Das, D. & Chatterjee, P. (2015). Library Automation : An Overview. *International journal of research in library science*, 1(1), 1-7.
- [3] J, N. (2019). A study on library automation status among the aided college in Bengaluru. *Library Philosophy and practice(e-journal)*.
- [4] Jharotia, A. (2020). Library Automation essential for Digital Era. *Quality Enhancement and employability in Higher education : A Holostic approach*, 100-116.
- [5] Kent, A. (1997). *Encyclopedia of Library & Information Science*. Marcel Dekker, 19.
- [6] Matonkar, P. &. (2021). Study of Library Automation and computing skills of Library Professional in Goa. *Library philosophy and practice (e-journal)*.
- [7] Muniraja, A. (2021). Library Automation- An Introduction. *International journal of search in library science*, 7(2), 192-198.
- [8] Patel, S. (2014). Library Automation: An overview. *International journal of Research in Humanities and social sciences*, 02(05), 35-40.
- [9] Sivankalai, S. (2020). Awareness of library Automation among the professionals in Academic libraries at state of Eritrea. *International journal of academic library and Information science*, 8(1), 17-21.
- [10] Ukachi, Ngozi B., N, V.N. & O, U.D. (2014). Library Automation and use of open source software to maximize library effectiveness. *Information and knowledge management*, 3(4), 74-82.

WHAT IS WELLNESS?

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Introduction

Wellness is a modern word with ancient roots. The key tenets of wellness as both preventive and holistic can be traced back to ancient civilizations from the East (India, China) to the West (Greece, Rome). In 19th-century Europe and the United States, a variety of intellectual, religious and medical movements developed in parallel with conventional medicine. With their focus on holistic and natural approaches, self-healing and preventive care, these movements have provided a firm foundation for wellness today. Wellness-focused and holistic modalities have gained more visibility since the 1960s/1970s under the writings and thought leadership of an informal network of US physicians and thinkers (such as Halbert Dunn, Jack Travis, Don Ardell, Bill Hettler, and others). As these have evolved, proliferated, and gone mainstream, they have informed the healthy-living, self-help, self-care, fitness, nutrition, diet and spiritual practices that have become a flourishing wellness movement in the 21st century.

Defining Wellness

“.. a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.” – The World Health Organisation.

“ The active pursuit of activities , choices and lifestyles that lead to a state of holistic health.” – The Global Wellness Institute. There are two important aspects to this definition. First, wellness is not a passive or static state but rather an “active pursuit” that is associated with intentions, choices and actions as we work toward an optimal state of health and wellbeing. Second, wellness is linked to holistic health—that is, it extends beyond physical health and incorporates many different dimensions that should work in harmony. Wellness is often confused with terms such as health, wellbeing and happiness. While there are common elements among them, wellness is distinguished by not referring to a static state of being (i.e., being happy, in good health, or a state of wellbeing). Rather, wellness is associated with an active process of being aware and making choices that lead toward an outcome of optimal holistic health and wellbeing.

Principles of Wellness

Adams (2003) has defined four main principles of wellness:

- 1) Wellness is multi dimensional
- 2) Wellness research and practice should be oriented toward identifying causes of wellness rather than causes of illness.
- 3) Wellness is about balance
- 4) Wellness is relative, subjective and perceptual.

Wellness is Multidimensional

Wellness includes seven dimensions.

- 1) Social: It is the ability to relate to and connect with other people in our world. Connecting and engaging with others and our communities in meaningful ways.
- 2) Emotional: It is the ability to understand ourselves and cope with challenges life can bring. Being aware of, accepting and expressing our feelings, and understanding the feelings of others.
- 3) Spiritual: It is the ability to establish peace and harmony in our life. Searching for meaning and higher purpose in human existence.
- 4) Environmental: It is the ability to make a positive impact on the quality of our environment is it our homes, our communities to our Environmental Wellness. Fostering positive interrelationship between planetary health and human actions, choices and wellbeing.
- 5) Physical: It is the ability to maintain a healthy quality of life that allows us to get through our daily activities without undue fatigue or physical stress. Nourishing a healthy body through exercise, nutrition, sleep, etc.

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- 6) Occupational: It is the ability to get personal fulfillment from our jobs or our chosen career fields while still maintaining balance in our lives.
- 7) Mental/ Intellectual: It is the ability to open our minds to new ideas and experiences that can be applied to personal decisions, group interaction and community betterment. Engaging the world through learning, problem-solving, creativity, etc.

The Wellness Continuum

One way to understand wellness is to consider health as a continuum that extends from illness to a state of optimal wellbeing. On one end, patients with poor health engage the medical paradigm to treat illnesses; they interact reactively and episodically with doctors and clinicians who provide care. On the opposite end, people focus proactively on prevention and maximizing their vitality. They adopt attitudes and lifestyles that prevent disease, improve health, and enhance their quality of life and sense of wellbeing. In other words, wellness is proactive, preventive and driven by self-responsibility. The growth of wellness is the extension of this consumer value and worldview. Wellness is different from healthcare. Our healthcare systems use a pathogenic and reactive approach, focused on causes, consequences, diagnosis and treatment of diseases and injuries. In contrast, wellness is a salutogenic and proactive approach, focused on prevention, healthy lifestyles and the pursuit of optimal wellbeing. Ultimately, a solid foundation for wellness helps us prevent and overcome disease, both at present and in the future.

Wellness vs. Wellbeing

The terms “wellness,” “wellbeing” and “happiness” have often been used together or interchangeably by businesses, researchers and the media. This graphic outlines what they share in common and how these terms differ in concept, usage and association.

S.No	Wellness	Well being
1	Relates to intention, action, and activities.	Perceptions of the state of being
2	Has a prominent physical dimension	Has a prominent mental/emotional dimension
3	Associates with healthy lifestyles.	Associates with feelings of satisfaction and sense of fulfillment

Importance of Wellness in Schools

Why is wellness important in schools? We could focus on impacts of wellness on test scores or classroom management. We could illustrate the advantages relating to productivity, classroom communities, or teacher relationships. While we will touch on many of these benefits, the most important reason to care about wellness is that we, as teachers, have been trusted with the world’s most valuable resource: children. Each student who frustrates us, confuses us, delights us, and impresses us has intrinsic worth and potential. It is a sobering and significant stewardship to be a part of the classroom/school community life that prepares children to “[inherit] resources of the race, and to use [their] own powers for social ends” (Dewey, 1897, p. 78). Thus we should focus first and foremost on wellness because we truly care about the students entrusted to us, recognize our moral obligation to nurture those within our stewardship, and want the best for them both now and in the future. Students are not the only ones who benefit from wellness on the agenda. Teachers who persist with low levels of personal wellness are more exhausted, more cynical, and more distant from their students. They question their own self-efficacy, limit their own achievements, are demotivated when faced with challenges, and are more likely to experience burn-out. In contrast, teachers who enjoy wellbeing are better able to interact, teach, and achieve (Bentea, 2017). In some cases, prioritizing wellness may only require a few changes to classrooms, procedures, and priorities, but these changes can lead to long- lasting positive impacts for both students and teachers. Overall wellness enhances intrinsic motivation, decreases disciplinary problems, increases academic achievement, improves school satisfaction and leads to flourishing of individuals, communities, and nations (Buecker et al., 2018). Fostering and teaching wellness is a way to show students and educators we care about them and want to

support them by enabling them with short- and long-term benefits.

Conclusion

Wellness is an individual pursuit—we have self-responsibility for our own choices, behaviors and lifestyles—but it is also significantly influenced by the physical, social and cultural environments in which we live. We have the opportunity to formally teach our students to maximize their potential, and prioritizing their wellness is a good place to start. Our first step in enabling our students and educators with the power of wellness is to assess it. Then respond to the assessment in ways informed by research and adapted to our context. The resources that follow will help us start or continue our efforts to optimize our school's potential as a place of learning and flourishing. Promoting the healthy development of all students, as well as enabling all students to reach their potential, is a priority for educators in schools. Students' health and wellness contribute to their ability to learn in all disciplines, including health and physical education, and that learning, in turn, contributes to their overall wellness. Social and emotional learning is a process through which students acquire and effectively apply the knowledge and understanding necessary to develop self-awareness, self-management, relationship skills, social awareness and responsible decision making.

References

- [1] Bentea, C. (2017). Teacher self-efficacy, teacher burnout and psychological well-being. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences*, 1128–1136. <https://edtechbooks.org/-PGj>
- [2] Buecker, S., Nuraydin, S., Simonsmeier, B., Schneider, M. & Luhmann, M. (2018). Subjective well-being and academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Personality* 74. <https://edtechbooks.org/-PHzN>
- [3] Dewey, J. (1987). My pedagogic creed. *The School Journal*, 54(3), 77–80.
- [4] IPEN. (n.d.). Why is wellbeing important in schools? Home page. <https://edtechbooks.org/-PGj> About Wellness. National Wellness Institute. Available from: <https://nationalwellness.org/resources/multicultural-competency-in-wellness/> Accessed 25
- [5] January 2023
- [6] Difference Between Health and Wellness. Available from: <http://www.differencebetween.com/difference-between-health-and-vs-wellness/> Accessed 25
- [7] January 2023
- [8] World Health Organization: The determinants of health. Available from: <http://www.who.int/hia/evidence/doh/en/> Accessed 25 January 2023

SOCIAL MEDIA AND TEACHING PROFESSIONALS: BOON'S AND THREATS

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Abstract

Every teaching professionals should integrate their computing skills into their pedagogical practice, encouraging constructivism, promoting collaborative learning among the pupils and identify the individual differences and develop instructional materials from online and offline sources and give the best from the students and contribute to the learning society. Using social media for teaching is a necessary not sufficient requirement for developing the knowledge and skills in the 21st century. Obviously many instructors are successfully in this way, but there is still a great deal of resistance to such radical change. Social media is here to facilitate and increase access to developing social media must go along with developing pedagogical innovation and unity.

Introduction

Technology is a powerful tool that is transforming education. Technology, with its various application, has rapidly revolutionized all aspects of our everyday lives. It has slowly but surely also made an impact on education and how we shape young minds. And as is always the case with technology, some institutions have embraced it, and while some continue to resist it for various reasons. Technology has the ability to transform education. Since today's generation is so tech savvy, students get engaged with what they are doing improve learning outcomes with technology. In the present scenario, there is very easy access to information with technology. The teacher here takes on the role of facilitator and guide so as to facilitate students with the right approach of managing abundant information to their optimum benefit and in taking right decisions in the technologically complex world. In the tech savvy society teachers role becomes very essential as they make students learn how to evaluate the abundant information available critically, to identify facts from propaganda, to understand the real ethical, legal and moral issues with respect to the access and use of information to create meaning from data. Social media is a great resource for teachers to improve teaching, get inspired, and connect with the other educators. Each social media platform offers many different ways to be used in the classroom, from sharing announcements to holding live lectures and so much more. Social media provides a smoother, more direct communication tool between students, teachers and parents, who can check in and ask or respond to question and also to help and to built a healthy relation between them. Accountability of teachers has enhanced due to the coming of social media, through various ways like relationship building, career development of both students and teachers.

Benefits of Social Media for Teaching Professionals

As an educator, you know that technology is a huge part of the classroom. Social media is, without a doubt, one of the most technologies that students use. As a result, it can be incredibly beneficial for educators to social media in the classroom, whether its Twitter, Facebook or Instagram here are five way that educators can benefit from these platforms. Engage with students: Students are constantly on social media, educator can use this advantage by engaging with these platforms. Educators can also use social media to answer students questions outside of class. Create a robust learning community whether the students are their Facebook friends. Get Feedback from students: Social media is also a great way to get feedback from students through platforms like Twitter and Facebook to poll their students or ask for their opinion on certain topics. Share resources with students: One of the best things about social media is that it's a great way to share resources with students. Educators can post links to articles, videos, and other materials to help them learn and also use social media to share their resources, like lesson plans and hand outs. This is a great way to ensure that your students have everything they need to be successful. Connect with other educators: Social media is also a great way to connect with other educators. This is a great way to get new ideas for their classroom. It's also a great way to learn about new products and technologies that can benefit their students. Build a Professional learning Network: A Professional Learning Network (PLN) is an excellent way for educators to connect and learn from another. Twitter is an excellent platform for building a PLN. Educators can also use social media to join professional development opportunities. These can be live events or online courses that will help you learn new strategies and techniques for your classroom.

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Social Media Do's and Don'ts for a Teaching Professionals

Social Media is a two-sided coin. It can be damaging for your career and well-being but also a source of great positivity and job.

Do share useful advice with other Teachers: Asking your colleagues is a great first step to get some help if you're stuck on a topic or idea. However, if that fails, you always turn to social media to get advice from fellow teachers who are just like you.

Don't post about Individual students at the end of a hard day, its tempting to log on to Twitter and rant about different students. It goes without saying, but you should never do this.

It's important to protect the anonymity of any student you teach

It looks unprofessional and could lead to negative feedback

Do interact with teachers you look up to social Media is a great way to interact with teachers that don't work at your school. Educators got an information about the working style of other teachers.

Don't post a picture without a parent consent educators have the best intentions must post the class pictures on the school Facebook account. It's important to get written consent from every single parent before hand.

Do post your best displays educator displays their classroom experience through social media. Due to this, they can save their time at the same time, students should get a clear-cut information related to that topic

Don't post about your private life on a public account educators post thousands of inspiring stories and pieces of advice on Twitter ever around Education doesn't share details of their private life.

Do Be Honest social media is filled with teacher accounts that depict a Pinterest - perfect lifestyle. Don't share sensitive personal information, it's good to be honest about their experience online. If they are struggling and reach out, other teachers might be able to help and giving some comforting words.

Don't interact with students don't accept students requests in social media

Do stay professional be a good professional, Educators should maintain a professional attitude towards their profession, colleagues, stakeholders and to the society

Don't Let your life revolve around social media is designed to keep them engaged and returning for more. It is easy to slip into the habit of looking at social media every hour of the day. In order to develop a healthy relationship with social media, try to fixed the time limit for using social media.

Encourage students to make the most of their Social media make sure students should understand the power of branding creative story telling and digital awareness - all a massively part of today's success

Don't Tag other Teachers it's great to have a good time with your co-workers. It's also generally a good idea for any professional to keep really good times with co- workers off social media

Boon's of Using Social Media for Teacher Educators

Social networks are empowering students and educational institutions with opportunities to improving teaching - learning process. Slide Share, Quora and Research Gate etc, are helping students by providing online tutorials. These platforms offer valuable resource material for enriching knowledge base. Social media is also a medium where students can establish beneficial connections for their careers. As an educational institution, it is crucial to be active in many social platforms possible, this helps to create better student engagement strategies and makes learning more interactive and inclusive. In this context social media has a lot to offer to the educational community. Here are some of the direct benefits of social media usage for the academic world. Collaborative Learning: On Social media, students exchange lot of information. By doing this, they get engaged with each other and learn how to manage projects and coordinate with teams sitting globally among with cross cultural sensitivities. Similarly, the use of social media has made it easier and faster to interact with peers or teachers about class-related topics. These methods has been adopted by teacher students in their classroom. Information sharing by students: Teacher students are continuously hooked on to the internet through their smart phones and hence rapidly transmit information to their connections. Apart from just sharing views and opinions they also exchange lot of valuable information. This information is a lot more than just interesting videos or snapshots and cover useful stuff related to their studies.

They exchange helpful information for the classes and examination. Social Media Marketing for Educators: For educational institutions, social media is a great marketing tool to reach out to the prospective students. This new media has led education professionals to build a strong marketing strategy to increase brand awareness. Colleges allover the world are extensively carrying out social media strategies to tap students. Helps to Foster research: Social media offers collaborative opportunities to foster research initiatives. It is one of the best

platforms to extract secondary data. Can conduct survey pools to gather sampling people and other experts on a particular subject. Social media can help academic researchers compile and produce useful content by working on collaboration assignment and projects. Continue Teaching from Anywhere and Everywhere: It is difficult to address queries of students during classroom sessions. This makes it further difficult for students to clear doubts. Teacher educator can take advantage of social media technology to extend teaching hours beyond classroom. They can setup Facebook Live Series or Twitter discussions to cover unbiased doubts of their students. Take Advantage of Blogs to create Virtual library: Setting up a personal blog or website gives professors a lot of freedom to build intellectual credibility. They can upload their academic work and other important lectures and videos that will allow students to take relevant inputs as reference materials for their students. Let students learn from Social networking: Social media offer great learning opportunities through social networking. Students can be encouraged to build networks to support professional help in career. Teacher educators can also connect with the teacher students and help them identify suitable job openings in various institutions and final relevant connections for their future generation.

Conclusion

Social media has negative and positive impact on today's world. The traditional classroom learning method that has a teacher standing on a podium in front of rows of students is still prevalent. The use of automated technological platforms is on the rise, be it in the form of virtual or online learning software or other digital resources used to enhance teaching and learning in the classroom. Teaching and Learning become more interactive. Social media builds the social relationship in everyone. Students should maintain their relationship outside the school, on the other side students face dangerous situation through talking to strangers, affect their academic achievement too.

References

- [1] Rahul Jain (2019). Use of Social media in Teaching And Learning : Emerging Role of Social media And its Importance in Teaching and Learning. <https://www.asmaindia.in/blog>.
- [2] Thanavathi. S., (2014). Integrating Social Media in Teacher Education. Published in : Teacher Education in 21st century, Issue and Concerns. Renu Publishers. New Delhi
- [3] Stefania Manra & Maria Ranieri (2014). Teacher's Professional development in online social networking sites; Social network sites in professional development. World Conference on Educational Multimedia, Hypermedia and Telecommunications 2014
- [4] <https://www.twinkl.com.sg/blog>
- [5] <https://www.iedunote.com/5>

SELF-CONFIDENCE OF THE HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE HYBRID CLASSROOM

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Abstract

The world has been witnessing many changes and innovations, especially in the educational field after COVID-19. The impact of technological changes on the psychology of the learner plays a vital role since the confidence level of the young learner has been tossed between the pandemic and the online class. Hybrid classrooms are one of the changes which we are all witnessing. The study is carried out to know the self-confidence level of the students, who have been witnessing the hybrid classroom due to the pandemic. A questionnaire consisting of 15 questions was sent through Google Forms. The sample consisted of 32 students studying higher secondary students. The results are found to be convincing through proper measures and expose the students to gain confidence and break their fears.

Introduction

Competence, knowledge, and performance are interconnected ideas that are essential for people to succeed in their careers. Each person might encounter several difficulties in life as a result of the absence of confidence. Without any of these, people may have a number of difficulties in accomplishing the objectives set out by their recognized institutions or their own personal objectives. The majority of the current problem in the educational system is brought on by poor self-confidence in a number of pupils, which causes them to participate insufficiently in class and make unsatisfactory development while spending a lot of time in it.

Literature Review

The attribute of a student that makes them feel confident about effectively completing various tasks both inside and outside of the classroom for educational purposes is known as self-confidence. The researcher's findings on the influence of self-confidence on learning, however, suggest that students' learning styles differ depending on whether they have strong or low self-confidence. Functionally speaking, learning refers to a series of modifications to behaviour brought about by human experiences (Houwer, Holmes & M Moors, 2013). The act of involving students in activities and allowing them to gain knowledge through their sharing of experiences or by receiving information from the teacher is how they further describe learning. According to Perkins (2018), self-confidence is associated with success, educational accomplishments, conciliation, and a person's well-being. Self-confidence is defined as the belief or trust that a student has in their ability to complete something well (Kanza, 2016). Self-efficacy, self-esteem, and self-compassion are three qualities that may influence anyone's degree of confidence, among other things. Self-confidence is essential to psychological theories of motivation (Bandura, 1997; Eccles, 2009), and it has practical application in education. For instance, students' self-confidence has been linked to their interest in specific subjects and their decision-making regarding the courses they will take (Viljaranta, Tolvanen, Aunola, & Nurmi, 2014). (Regan and De Witt, 2015). The motives and self-confidence of students are then very important for teaching and policy in scientific education in England and many other nations, especially as more students are being drawn to science (The Royal Society, 2014).

Methodology

Numerous studies have concentrated on specific topics, particularly peer comparisons and subject comparisons (e.g. Marsh and Parker, 1984; Marsh et al., 2015a) (e.g. Marsh, 1986, Marsh et al., 2015b). Numerous studies have concentrated on particular structural models, such as those that model solely student-level achievement and class- or school-level average attainment to infer the effect of peer comparisons. A questionnaire consisting of 15 questions was sent through Google Forms. The sample consisted of 32 students studying higher secondary students to know their self-confidence level and performance with respect to certain situations like individual work, pair work, group work, technological aid, online platforms, projects, discussions, self-evaluation, adopting strategies, creating thinking, and applying concepts. A sample is a heterogenous group in terms of school, gender, boards, and medium of instruction.

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Discussion

The responses seem to be quite interesting. Students are confident enough to adopt to any kind of environment and challenges put forth to them and consistently progress accordingly. 32 students responded to the questionnaire for most of the questions, and more than 50 percent of the students either agreed or strongly disagreed.

For question 1, nearly 60% of the students responded that they are comfortable in engaging themselves in pair or group work. For questions, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 13, nearly 60% of the students stated, they are strongly comfortable in making strategies in groups, self-evaluating themselves, understanding and applying concepts, thinking creatively for more solutions, and so on.

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig 3

Fig 4

Fig 5

For questions 3, 7, 9, and 10, the response finds to positive that higher secondary students are good at doing work collaboratively, finding multiple solutions for a problem, evaluating their project, and keeping track of their achievements respectively.

Conclusion

The study clearly shows that confidence is an intra-personal skill that can be nurtured through proper practice. Academic success and self-confidence are mostly related. Students that do well in school typically possess a strong level of self-confidence and are able to do the necessary duties with ease, even during a pandemic like Covid-19. Academic success and self-confidence were shown to be positively correlated, the students with higher levels of self-confidence exhibit superior performance. Being confident in oneself is crucial, especially for students. Additionally, students gain confidence via cooperative learning in terms of association and engagement. However, in order for students to succeed, a hybrid mode must be provided to boost their level of confidence and allow them to showcase their skills in their academics and personal life.

References

- [1] Marsh et al., (2015). The big-fish-little-pond effect: generalizability of social comparison processes over two age cohorts from Western, Asian, and Middle Eastern Islamic countries. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107 (1) (2015), pp. 258-271.
- [2] E. Zell, Z. Krizan (2014) Do People Have Insight Into Their Abilities? A Metasynthesis. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 9 (2), pp. 111-125.
- [3] De Houwer, J., Barnes-Holmes, D., & Moors, A. (2013). What is learning? On the nature and merits of a functional definition of learning. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 20(4), 631-642.

A SURVEY ON STUDENTS PERCEPTION ON CLEAN INDIA MISSION IN DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract

A survey cum interview method is used to find students perception on clean India mission in digital era by using a standardized tool. The tool is standardized by researcher by item analysis method. A stratified random sampling technique is applied to collect sample of 630 students of Kurnool district. Mean, SD, t test and f-ratio statistical techniques are used on collected data, the data interpreted and analysed at 0.05 and 0.01 significant level. It is found that there is no significant impact among Boys and Girls on Swachh Bharath mission of Kurnool district high school students, but according to mean values the girls high school students are performing better than Boys of Kurnool district high school. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on Swachh Bharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on Swachh Bharath Abhiyan mission.

Keywords: Swachh Bharath, Students, T Test, Significant

Introduction

The Government of India launched the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, or Clean India Mission, in 2014 as a national initiative to end open defecation and improve solid waste management. It is a revamped version of the 2009-launched Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan, which Manmohan Singh's successor continued but which fell short of its goals (Swachh Bharat Mission, 2020). The effort, started by the Indian government, sought to build enough toilets to make India "open-defecation free" (ODF) by 2 October 2019, the 150th anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi's birth. During that time, an estimated 89.9 million toilets were constructed. Aside from eliminating manual scavenging, raising awareness about sanitation standards and changing people's behaviour were also goals of the mission's first phase. Another goal was to increase local capacity. The second stage of the mission is to maintain the absence of open defecation, enhance solid and liquid waste management, and enhance the working conditions for sanitation personnel (GoI, 2020). The mission aims to advance toward objective 6.2 of the sixth of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, which was created in 2015. Hindi is used for the campaign's official name. It means "Clean India Mission" in English. Prime Minister Narendra Modi formally inaugurated the campaign on October 2, 2014, at Rajghat in New Delhi. With three million government workers and students from all across India participating in 4,043 cities, towns, and rural villages, it is India's greatest cleaning initiative to date. The campaign was dubbed Satyagrah se Swachhagrah by the prime minister during a rally in Champaran in honour of Gandhi's Champaran Satyagrah, which began on 10 April 1916 (Satyagrah to Swachhagrah, 2018). The researcher made a survey on students perception on clean India mission in digital era.

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy

Fig 1 Sample Design

Tools

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the Impact of swachh bharath mission on high school students at kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the impact swachh Bharath Mission on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.
- 2) To find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district

Hypothesis

- 1) There would be no significant difference between impact swachh Bharath Mission among Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district
- 2) There would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district

Fig 2. Sample size of gender and type of family

Results and Discussion

Hypothesis. There would be no significant difference between impact swatch Bharath Mission among Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.

Table 1 Means, SD's and t- values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their Gender.

Gender	N	Intensity scores		t-value
		Mean	SD	
Boys	356	112.90	19.43	0.1227@
Girls	274	119.70	20.89	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level.

The impact of swatch Bharath Abiyan of 356 Boys and 274 Girls of kurmool district are evaluated as follows. The Mean value of girls are greater than that of Boys. The mean and SD values of Boys are 112.90, 19.45 similarly the girl values are 119.70 and 20.89. The t value is 0.1227, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. There fore there is no significant difference between Boys and Girls high school students on the impact of swatch bharath mission ub Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that there is no significant impact among Boos and Girls on swatch bharath mission of Kurnool district high school students, but according to mean values the girls high school students are performing better than Boys of Kurnool district high school.

Fig 3.1. Mean and SD'values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their Gender.

Hypothesis. There would be no significant difference impact swatch Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district

Table 2: Means, SD's and t- values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their type of family.

Type of family	N	Intensity scores		t-value
		Mean	SD	
Joint Family	211	117.77	19.08	1.6941@
Nuclear Family	419	114.95	20.92	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level.

In the present study out of 630 high school students 211 students are living in joint family remaining 419 students are in nuclear family in Kurnool district. The mean and SD values of joint family students are 117.77 and 19.08, similarly for nuclear family students are 114.95 and 20.92. The mean value of joint family students

is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swachh nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District.

The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swachh nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swachh bharath abhiyan mission.

Fig 4 Mean and SD values by influence of swachh bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their type of family.

Conclusions

Hence it is concluded that there is no significant impact among Boys and Girls on swachh bharath mission of Kurnool district high school students, but according to mean values the girls high school students are performing better than Boys of Kurnool district high school. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swachh nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swachh bharath abhiyan mission.

References

- [1] Swachh Bharat Mission (Grameen) Phase 2 launched with an outlay of Rs 1.4 lakh crore". cnbctv18.com. 4 March 2020. Retrieved 21 December 2020.
- [2] Satyagraha to Swachhagrah: Narendra Modi addresses rally in Champaran". Business Standard. 10 April 2018. Archived from the original on 12 April 2018.

EDUCATION IN THE VEDIC GURUKUL TRADITION THAT IS HOLISTIC AND STUDENT-CENTERED

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Abstract

The ancient Indian Vedic Gurukuls and the different disputes that surround the nature of this system are both topics that are investigated in this research. First, the Gurukul system will be analysed through the perspective of current educational theory, including curriculum, pedagogy, and evaluation. After then comes the analysis and discussion of the controversies around the many features of such an educational system. This article introduces modern debates and points of contention on the student-centered dimension of the Gurukul System that flourished in the Indian subcontinent and provides a brief examination of the Vedic Gurukul System as a step in this direction. This article also serves as a step in this direction. These disputes typically centre on how the system stacks up against various current educational ideas, particularly in respect to cognitive achievement and personalization and contextualization of instruction (the latter being a thrust area in modern educational systems). The descriptions and concepts of the Gurukul system that are mentioned in ancient texts like the Vedas, Upanishads, Ramayana, Mahabharata, and the Puranas are the basis for a significant portion of the ongoing debates regarding the applicability of the Gurukul to contemporary educational structures. This is an important point to keep in mind. Such current discussions are crucial because they help validate the efficacy of the Gurukul system in all of its spatio-temporal dimensions and help draw ideas and inspiration to features that may be re-introduced to the present educational system.

Keywords: *Education, Tradition, Holistic, Student-Centered, Vedic*

Introduction

It appears that nations all over the world are coming to the realisation that education, in order for it to be successful, needs to be appropriate to the socio-economic and cultural context of the student or learner. As a result, nations are reverting back to their traditional approaches to education. Indigenous educational systems were successful because they evolved from the reality of the socio-economic and cultural context of the society at that time, and they also addressed the complex developmental needs of the individual learner regardless of age. This allowed indigenous educational systems to be successful. This holistic focus of Gurukul education system of India aimed to make every student (while taking into consideration the individual's ability, personality, and interests) a treasured member of the society. If a system of education can address the needs of the individual within the socioeconomic and cultural context of his or her society, then that system of education is considered to be student-centered and holistic. The pressing need in the modern world is to research such systems, their tenets, philosophies, and approaches, and learn from them so as to initiate and engage the learners with best practises that are appropriate to the society.

ऋचो अक्षरे परमे व्योमन्
यस्मिन् देवा अधि विश्वे निषेदुः ।
यस्तं न वेद किम् ऋचा करिष्यति
य इत्तद्विदुः त इमे समासते ॥ Rig Veda 1/164/39

The hymns of the Vedas describe the same all-pervasive, unbreakable ultimate truth in which all of the gods and goddesses are submerged. What use are the simple songs to the one who is ignorant of the reality? If he is able to comprehend this reality, then it will not be difficult for him to learn about the deities and other gods.

कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्ते मा फलेषु कदाचन ।
मा कर्मफलहेतुर्भूर्मा ते सङ्गोऽस्त्वकर्मणि ॥
श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता 2.47

It is not within your power to anticipate the benefits of such action; only to act is permissible on your part. Therefore, you should neither consider the prize to be the reason for acting in this manner, nor should you just sit about doing nothing. At its heart, the Vedic Education system adhered to a constructivist paradigm, in which students actively participated in their own education and formed meaning on the basis of their experiences

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and previous knowledge. The acquisition of knowledge of the Vedas, Vedangas, Brahmins, Upanishads, and other Shruti books was necessary in order to achieve the ultimate goal of the Vedic system of education, which was the understanding of the ultimate truth, also known as the nature of the Para Brahman.

मन्द्रा कृणुध्वं धियं आ तनुध्वं नावररत्रपरणीं कृणुध्वम।

इष्कृणुध्वम आयुधरं कृणुध्वं प्राञ्चं यज्ञं प्रणयता सखाय ॥

Be creative once you have written enticing poems, O followers; produce a variety of plants, construct oar-driven boats, practise right contemplation; design devastating weapons for the destruction of your crops; and continue to use fire to keep foes at bay, carrying out actions with the goal of improving the lives of other people.

The Vedic educational system has been regarded by a number of researchers as being of a totally

religious nature and, as a result, as being intended solely for the Brahmin priestly class. This assumption is partially accurate in the sense that the Samhita portion of the Rig, Yajur, and Sama Vedas (especially the latter two) dealt extensively with the various sacrifices that were performed and the roles that were played by the various types of priests who were responsible for performing these sacrifices. However, to characterise the Vedas as purely religious in nature would be a fallacy because the Vedas also contained knowledge pertinent to other fields such as philosophy, sociology, the humanities, science, and economics. This is because the Vedas were concerned with how to live, prosper, and attain Para Vidya through the Apar Vidya of the Vedic Samhita and the Upanishads. The Vedas were a source for understanding the history of the civilization since they documented the history of the Aryan people in India (different wars between tribes are recounted), and the Vedas were also a source for the history of India. In conclusion, the Atharva Veda was the source of inspiration for a great deal of the secular knowledge that made India famous before the Common Era. For instance, the Atharva Veda contains the germs of early medical philosophy. This text describes a variety of distinct sorts of medical practitioners and provides an early taxonomy of the many medical subspecialties. In the Buddhist tradition, the famed Sushruta, Charaka, and subsequently Jivaka expanded upon and refined this into a specialised stream of knowledge throughout time. As a result, reading the Vedas was obligatory for all members of Aryan society (although only Sudras and women were first granted access to the Vedas) since they included the fundamental information necessary for the majority of occupations. However, the amount of time a student was required to spend participating in obligatory Vedic study varied depending on their Varna.

Pedagogy

The Sravana-Manana-Nidhidhyasana model was the primary method of instruction that was utilised. In this model, the Acharya would first explain to the pupil a piece of the Vedic Samhita, which the student would then memorise (Sravana). The learner would then comprehend the meaning of the segment (Manana) and any uncertainties, if there were any, would be removed through a combination of Socratic conversation with the Acharya and individual thought. The final phase of Nidhidhyasana is where the learner mulls over the newly acquired information and makes an effort to incorporate it into the learning framework that he or she already has. Because the student would have have constructed a knowledge bank of previous learning during the course of the obligatory school era, this assimilation of new knowledge into existing schemas would be a significant part of higher education under the Vedic system. The Vedic system recognised that a single Acharya could not hold all knowledge, and as a result, it encouraged advanced students to seek out famous instructors located around the

realm who specialised in the subject area of their choosing. Conversations back and forth between the instructor and the student were also a common method of instruction utilised in more advanced levels of education. Quite frequently, the student would begin the conversation by querying the instructor about a specific topic (Prashna), and the instructor would then elaborate at length on the topic that was presented to them. The discussion takes the shape of a step-by-step series of questions and replies between the instructor and the student. In these exchanges, the instructor will employ various pedagogical strategies, such as anecdotes, parallels, parables, and so on, in order to convey a certain idea. The several Upanishads, such as the Kenopanishad and the Kathopanishad, provide detailed illustrations of these instruments. These phrases are used in the Taittiriya Brahmana, प्रशिनीण्ण questioner अभीप्रशिनीण्ण cross-questioner प्रश्नविवाक answerer to provide an explanation of this procedure. It is possible, given the nature of this kind of education, that it was frequently employed for advanced learning to explain and refine student uncertainties or to elaborate on a complicated subject or philosophy.

Assessment

का ते अस्त्यरमकृतिः सुकतैः कदा नूनं ते मघवन्दाशेम ।
विश्वा मतीराततने त्यावाधा म इन्द्र श्रणवो हवेमा ॥

O Gurudeva, you are the master of renown as well as wisdom! Could you please share with us some of the loveliest phrases that we should utilise to make you happy? When do you suggest that we give you the exam based on the information that we have gleaned? When will we be able to expand our knowledge with the help of your guidance and have our progress checked by you once more?

तानि कल्पद् ब्रह्मचारी सधलिलस्य पृष्ठे तपोऽधतिष्ठतप्यमानः समुद्रे ।
स स्नातो ब्रह्मः पिङ्गलः पृथिवयां बहु रोचते ॥

Throughout his time as a student, a student who had the gravity of the ocean always made it a point to perform acts of penance in order to atone for his transgressions against education. He appears to be in better physical shape and exudes an air of majesty now that he has completed his education and obtained the skills necessary to provide for himself financially.

तृणोल्कया ज्ञायते जातरूपम् वृत्तेन भद्रो व्यवहारेण साधुः ।
शुरो भव्येशवर्थकृच्छ्रेषु धीराः कृच्छ्रेष्वाप्सु सुहृदश्चारयश्च ॥
Viduraniti /Chapter 3

The gold is put through a fire test to determine its quality. Character is the hallmark of a morally upright guy. The behaviour of an individual is a reliable indicator of both their goodness and their wickedness, and similarly, one's bravery is most clearly seen in the face of hardship. When one is forced to endure hardship, they develop a greater capacity for forbearance. During times of struggle, both friends and adversaries will be put to the test.

The Sravana–Manana–Nidhidhyasana paradigm includes assessment as a component since the Acharya would do a continual, formative evaluation of the student's learning once the student had mastered each new segment of information. There is also the possibility of self-assessment through the mnemonic techniques of the Sravana stage. In this scenario, if there was an error of omission or addition in the verses (for instance, an extra syllable), then the mnemonic system would not work correctly and the student would be aware that an error had been introduced.

Contradictory Opinions Regarding The Student-Centered Approach Taken By The Gurukula System

The image that comes to mind when we think of the Gurukuls of old is that of a peaceful 'forest-university' (Chidbavananda, 1964) where individuals, in the Brahmacharya phase of their lives, entered leaving behind their family's social status (princes and paupers were equal here therefore hinting at the idea of social equality) and stayed together as a brotherhood under the watchful eyes of the Guru and Guru-Patni Along with ensuring that each of these kids created the intellectual capital necessary for a lifetime of success in a society, such social equality also insured that each of these students built the social and cultural capital essential for a lifetime of success in a society. The Ashram was self-sufficient in catering to the primary needs of the residents, and the goal of such an ashram was to assist students in becoming more well-rounded individuals while they were living amongst natural surroundings. This residential method had the benefit of allowing the Guru to monitor his wards unobtrusively in all aspects of their life. As a result, the Guru was able to adjust his instruction according to the needs of each individual learner. In addition to receiving formal education, students at the Gurukul also had the

opportunity to study and practise their skills in the natural laboratory that was provided for them by the environment. This afforded the Guru a multitude of opportunities to evaluate the students' level of comprehension of the material being taught and to select a course of study that was optimal for each individual student taking into account their strengths and areas of interest. During the course of the student's education, the Guru-Patni and the other inhabitants of the Gurukul, including the Guru himself, were responsible for providing their charges with pastoral care and acting in the role of foster parents for their charges. This all-encompassing method of educating and moulding people's personalities took into account every part of the individual and was exceptionally well-suited to the culture that prevailed at that era. The student-centred focus of the Gurukul system has been dismantled by contemporary academics, and its applicability to the modern world has been called into doubt on the basis of a number of interesting variables, which are as follows: In the Ashram system, the first stage (roughly the first eight years of an individual's life) is characterised by learning how to live independently. The next stage is typically a time to acquire knowledge and a preparation for living a life that is fulfilled. The final stage is characterised by learning how to live a life that is meaningful. Students were required to spend some time in gurukulavasam, also known as residency in the abode of the teacher, at this stage, which was referred to as the Brahmacharya Ashram. There is some disagreement among academics on what precisely gurukulavasam was and, more significantly, what it provided the student with. This is a topic that is relevant in modern times. Some academics believe that the knowledge acquired in the Gurukul was primarily limited to the memorization of religious texts and other religious matters (Seshagiri, 2010), but others assert that the Gurukulavasam was more all-encompassing and provided students with both religious and spiritual knowledge (Paravidya) as well as knowledge of the world (Aparavidya), (Sreekala Devi & Pillai, 2012).

There is also the question of whether or not the Gurukul method fostered just rote learning due to the fact those texts were committed to memory (Seshagiri, 2010). This is another topic that has been the subject of controversy. It is commonly believed that the learning process begins with the instructor, and that pupils only serve as receptacles for the information that is imparted to them. This is frequently contrasted unfavourably with contemporary educational theories such as "activity based learning" and "student led learning," both of which are praised for placing the emphasis on the learner. The Brhadaranyaka Upanishad, on the other hand, suggests that education is a three-part process that consists of Sravana (listening to the teacher), manana (assimilation by the student through contemplation and reflection), and nidhidhyasana (concentrated contemplation of the truth in order to realise it) (Sreekala Devi & Pillai, 2012). With this approach, the student becomes the primary focus of the educational experience, and the teacher acts more in the capacity of a facilitator and resource person. In addition, in order for the students to advance to higher levels of study, they were required to exhibit shraddha, which translates to commitment and steadfastness. This left the students responsible of charting their own path through the educational system (Chidbavananda, 1964).

In a similar vein, issues over flexibility and inclusiveness are also topics that turn out to be contentious sources of controversy. On the other hand, they were pillars of the educational concept that was widespread in the schooling of ancient Indians. Literature that is currently available suggests that there were two areas where such flexibility was very apparent: a) the age of entry into the Gurukulavasam and duration of stay, and b) the customization of teaching pedagogy based on the ability and interest displayed by students. Both of these factors are examples of areas where such flexibility was very apparent. According to Sreekala Devi and Pillai (2012), the typical age of enrolment into the programme was the eighth year of an individual's life; however, the age of entry might be extended all the way up to the twelfth year, depending on how prepared the student was. The length of the apprenticeship varied according to the objective (which was typically connected to the student's intended line of work) and might be anywhere from twelve years (for the goal of studying one Veda) to forty-eight years (mastering all four Vedas). The evidences that are accessible in a variety of texts, beginning with the Vedas, address the subject of how to properly recognise the range of skills and interests that are present among students while still maintaining an inclusive environment. According to Mookherji (1999), the aig eda makes the observation that "classmates or sakhya (those of same knowledge or who have studied the same Sastras) may have equality in the possession of their senses like the eye and ear, but betray inequality in respect to their power or speed of mind or the knowledge or wisdom which is attained by mind" (pg 25-26). He goes on to add that pupils were classified according to their abilities, with some having Mahaprajnan (high ability), others having Madhyamaprajnan (middle ability), and some having Alpaprajnan (poor ability) (low ability). The Gurus took into account the varying capacities of their students and adapted the subject matter as well as the instructional strategies to meet the needs of each individual pupil. The latter included activities such as self-study, listening to Parishads or conferences of learned men, practical sensorial experience, question and answer sessions between teacher and student, fables and stories from texts such as the Upanishads, and other similar activities depending on the subject

and individual student (Avinashilingam, 1997).

In addition to the focus on academic accomplishment, this discussion also addresses the issue of how the Gurukul system may foster holistic, student-centered growth. Additionally, the Gurukul system catered to the students' total well-being by addressing the emotive needs of the individual, fostering a feeling of spiritual well-being, and encouraging physical education. Mayr and Ulrich (2009) identified six components that contribute to an individual's level of happiness. These components are as follows: a) Making contact (establishing healthy relationships), b) Pleasure in exploration (recognising that one's surroundings provide a secure foundation for venturing out into the world), c) Self-control and mindfulness, d) Emotional stability, e) Self-assertiveness, and f) Task orientation. The Gurukul method, which was used in India, was based on similar ideas and aimed to help pupils develop holistically in addition to improving their academic performance. The Gurukuls were often set in the middle of a remote forest and offered their pupils the opportunity to investigate a variety of regulated situations. The pupils, in addition to their academic work, also took part in other duties; as a result, they were already becoming ready for the responsibilities of adult life (Chidbavananda, 1964). The other residents of the Ashram, such as the Guru-Patni, older disciples of the Guru, and so on, took care of the young wards and developed meaningful connections with them, which enabled the students to acquire emotional maturity and a sense of safety. The student's peers, regardless of their class or location, helped to build a sense of equality, which, in turn, assisted the student in developing assertiveness and confidence. In conclusion, the specific tasks that were set by the Guru assisted in the development of the student's task orientation, and the positive discipline assisted in the student's ability to muster physical alertness and self-control. This individual's total physical and emotional well-being served as a springboard for them to develop a feeling of spiritual well-being for themselves.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Gurukul system imbedded itself within the socio-cultural, economic & moral context of that era and related its curriculum to that context. As a result, the various elements of pedagogy that developed were concerned with providing a student-centered education that was holistic in nature. Understanding the holistic nature of the Gurukul system of that era through the critical lens of modern educational paradigms and thoughts is vitally important. Particularly important are aspects such as cognitive instruction, character building, customising and tailoring such an education to the needs of the learner, pastoral care and affective development, physical development, a sense of belonging, a relationship with the natural world, and social consciousness. Last but not least, it is essential that we extract the lessons that may be learned from this system by the education models of today, so that they are suitable to the philosophies and socio-cultural realities of our period.

References

- [1] Avinashilingam TS. Educational Philosophy of Swami Vivekananda. Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya 1964.
- [2] Chidbavananda S. The Indian National Education. Tapovanam Publishing House 1964.
- [3] Mookherji RK. Ancient Indian Education: Brahmanical & Buddhist. Cosmos Publications, India 1999;1:xlx
- [4] Seshagiri KM. A Cultural Overview of Education in Hindu Civilization. Handbook of Asian education: A cultural perspective. Zhao.Y., Lei. J., Li. G., He. M. F., Okano, K., Megahed, N., Gamage.D. & Ramanathan. H. (Eds.). Routledge 2010.
- [5] Sreekala Devi S, Pillai KNM. Genesis and Evolution of Education in Ancient India. Pragati Quarterly Research Journal 2012, 14-34.

ENHANCING SELF-EFFICACY OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING

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Abstract

Self-directed learning encourages the organic growth of self-assurance, initiative, tenacity, and life happiness. Self-directed learning is more efficient than "one size fits all" training because it enables everyone to address their specific knowledge gaps and upskill according to their particular roles and goals. Self-efficacy influences our goals, how we achieve those goals, and how we evaluate our performance. In this study, the investigator intends to enhance the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students through self-directed learning. The investigator adopted the experimental method, pre-test post-test non-equivalent design was employed, and a sample of 120 higher secondary commerce school students was selected for the present study. The investigator developed a self-directed learning package based Garrison model of self-directed learning for higher secondary commerce students. A self-efficacy scale was administered to determine whether a self-directed learning package effectively enhanced the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students. The study's findings revealed that a self-directed learning package in commerce effectively enhances self-efficacy of higher secondary school students.

Introduction

Self-directed learning, in its broadest sense, refers to a person's capacity to take the initiative to identify his or her own learning needs, capacity to set learning objectives, capacity to define the learning resources they require, capacity to choose/use effective learning strategies, and capacity to evaluate learning outcomes with or without help from a third party (Knowles, 1975). Individuals organize, carry out, and evaluate their learning experiences on their own when they engage in self-directed learning (Merriam et al., 2007). The obligation to learn changes from an external source—a teacher, for example—to the learner in self-directed learning. Crucial to this process is the learner's active participation and control over the learning environment (Boyer and Usinger, 2015; Grover, 2015). Learning conceptualized, designed, implemented, and evaluated by learners themselves is referred to as self-directed learning. (Brookfield, 2009). Radial & Volet (2009) define self-directed learning simply as "learning how to learn."

Self-directed learning is a style of instruction in which students manage their learning activities. Along with this, self-directed learning could be seen as a goal that students aspire to attain. Individuals embrace their particular individuality and preferences to accomplish it and take ownership of their learning (Kaufman, 2003). In self-directed learning, learners have greater independence in setting their learning objectives and determining how to complete tasks. Self-directed learning strongly emphasizes the importance of learners' initial and ongoing desire and resolve to work toward their objectives (Nadi et al., 2011). For most individuals, self-directed learning is the best approach to picking up new skills, knowledge, attitudes, and experiences. Moral independence, as well as a variety of emotional and intellectual traits, can be displayed by self-directed persons (Murray, 2015). The self-directed learning process should be designed with the individual's intellectual characteristics and critical thinking skills (Hendricson, 2006).

SDL refers to all learning undertaken by the students outside the classroom context. Self-directed learning has become synonymous with other pedagogical terms such as autonomous, self-managed, lifelong, and independent learning (Robbins 1988). Self-directed change is an intentional change in an aspect of who you are (i.e., the Real), whom you want to be (i.e., the Ideal), or both. Self-directed learning is a self-directed change in which you know and understand the change process. Self-directed learning skills are associated with lifelong learning. For students to obtain desirable outcomes, self-directed learning is necessary and absolute. Activities must be understood as teaching opportunities for students to gain personal responsibility. Organizing classroom learning is crucial, and teachers should use this to support their students' growth in autonomous learning (Suknaisith, 2014). Learning considered to be self-directed involves students making decisions about their own needs, learning goals, experiences, resources, and testing procedures.

Several circumstances influence pupils' self-directed learning, which is why problems at the top may

arise. According to Basri (1996), both internal and external influences can have an impact on a student's self-directed learning. Self-efficacy, drive to learn, attitudes, interests, and learning habits are examples of factors that originate within the students and are, therefore, psychic factors. Factors that affect the environment, socioeconomics, teachers, curriculum, subject matter, and infrastructure on which the student is not solely dependent. Not without cause, problems at the top acknowledge that several circumstances influence students' self-directed learning.

The process of learning is significantly influenced by self-efficacy. When a student is learning, self-efficacy is the idea that they will be able to complete assignments, plan their learning activities, and live in the expectation that they and others will succeed academically. Many circumstances influence pupils' self-directed learning, which is why problems at the top may arise (Baron & Byrne, 2004). When self-efficacy is high, it is necessary to complete tasks successfully, fulfill educational obligations, engage in physical activity and good health, engage in political activity, and refrain from acting up (Baron & Byrne, 2004). A key aspect in fostering kids' development and success in their environment. The learning environment is hostile since it contains all the items that students come into contact with when engaging in learning activities and impacts particular people (Hamalik, 2003).

Additionally, one of the vital psychological components is self-efficacy, and because of this, inappropriate role-playing behavior is frequently seen as crucial in many different branches of psychology. In reality, increasing self-efficacy and recognizing the elements influencing it will benefit learners' accomplishment. Self-efficacy is the capacity to meet problems in life. The degree or strength of one's confidence in their capacity to complete activities and achieve goals is known as self-efficacy (Ormrod, 2006). Bandura's (1977) Self-efficacy is the conviction that one can complete a task or succeed in a particular situation. One's perception of self-efficacy can significantly impact how one approaches objectives, projects, and obstacles (Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2020). The ability to perceive self-efficacy matures during adolescence (Zimmerman & MartinezPons, 1990).

Basereh & Pishkar's (2016) results found a positive relationship between self-efficacy and self-directed learning among advanced EFL students. Researchers Lema and Agrusa (2008) discovered that students' self-efficacy in the hospitality industry supported their theory that self-efficacy might strongly predict students' self-directed learning. Previously, Bandura (1994) mentioned that self-efficacy is a process that starts individuals in controlling learning. Meanwhile, the same thing was also expressed by Brokett & Hiemstra (1991) that self-efficacy is a readiness to improve students' self-directed learning. Understanding self-efficacy as a significant predictor of self-directed learning can help schools to provide efficient and practical training for students

The investigator found a relationship between self-directed learning and self-efficacy from the various research pieces. However, the investigator concluded from the various pieces of research that there is no self-directed learning package for enhancing self-efficacy. The investigator has observed that the learners take less initiative to learn or generate knowledge because they believe they can,t acquire their goal. So the investigator felt an immense need to develop a self-directed learning package to enhance the learner's self-efficacy to achieve their future goals somewhat. The investigator intended to check the effectiveness of the self-directed learning package by framing the following objectives, hypothesis, and methodology

Hypothesis Formulated for the Study

- 1)Self-directed learning is effective in enhancing the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students

Objectives of the Study

- 2)To develop a self-directed learning package in commerce for higher secondary school students.
- 3)To find out the effect of self-directed learning package in enhancing the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students

Methodology in Brief

In the present study, Self-Directed Learning is the independent variable, and self-efficacy is the dependent variable. To find the effect of the Self-Directed Learning Package in enhancing the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students, the investigator adopted an experimental method for the present study. Pre-test post-test non-equivalent groups design in the experimental section was selected. The investigator selected 120 higher secondary school students, of which 60 comprise the control group and 60 comprise the experimental group. Cluster sampling techniques were used for the present study. The investigator used the learning package in business studies based on self-directed learning, a lesson plan based on discussion and demonstration, and a self-efficacy scale for collecting the data. The investigator considered the base of the Garrison model, i.e., three phases:

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Phase 1: Self-Management, Phase 2: Self-Monitoring, and Phase 3: Motivation for preparing Self-Directed Learning Package. The Self-efficacy scale was prepared based on Bandura's four sources that may develop and alter Self-efficacy beliefs, i.e., Mastery Experiences, Vicarious Experiences, Social Persuasion, and Physiological and Emotional States. The investigator used descriptive statistics, t-test, and ANCOVA using SPSS for further statistical analysis.

Design and Development of a Self-Directed Learning Package

The main objective of the package is:

- 1) To enhance the self-efficacy of higher secondary school students.

For the systematic progress of research work, the investigator prepared a general design for the package. The ADDIE model is a framework used by instructional designers and developers. The five phases of the ADDIE model serve as a descriptive framework for developing helpful training and performance support tools.

- 1) Analysis: Need Analysis
- 2) Design- Designing of Self-directed learning Materials based on Garrison's model of Self-Directed Learning
- 3) Development: Development of a Self-directed learning package prepared ten lessons based on the prepared designed material of self-directed learning
- 4) Implementation: The prepared Self-directed learning package was implemented in the represented Sample selected
- 5) Evaluation: Administering the Self-efficacy scale

Preparation of General Format of Lesson Transcript Based on Prepared Package

The investigator prepared a general format of lesson transcript based on a self-directed design as

- 1) A general introduction with details of the teacher, student, class, and unit
- 2) Content analysis in terms of facts, concepts, principles, rules, process
- 3) Teacher expectations in terms of self-directed learning
- 4) Prerequisites related to the topic
- 5) Supporting materials: videos, pictures, usual classroom aids
- 6) Evaluation

Lesson transcripts were based on the prepared package. The investigator selected a topic from plus two business studies textbooks prepared by SCERT.

Procedure Adopted for the Study

In order to test the effectiveness of the Self-Directed Learning Package, the investigator used the following tool

- 1) Self-efficacy scale

The investigator selected a pre-test post-test non-equivalent group design to test the package's effectiveness. The prepared self-directed learning package was administered to a representative sample of 120 students at the higher secondary level. After administering the pre-test, both groups the sample was divided into control and experimental groups. The control group was given a discussion and demonstration lesson transcript. The self-directed learning package in commerce was exposed to the experimental group.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Descriptive Statistics of Self-Efficacy Scores of Higher Secondary School Students

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of self-efficacy scores of higher secondary school students

Descriptive statistics	pre-test scores of self-efficacy of control group	post-test scores of self-efficacy of control group	pre-test scores of self-efficacy of experimental group	post-test scores of self-efficacy of experimental group
N	54	54	54	54

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Mean	75.07	76.80	72.87	81.72
Std. Error of Mean	.933	.822	1.014	.652
Median	76.00	77.00	74.00	82.00
Mode	72	72	75	80
Std. Deviation	6.859	6.039	7.453	4.788
Skewness	.294	.082	-.531	-.033
Std. Error of Skewness	.325	.325	.325	.325
Kurtosis	-.330	1.017	.268	-.222
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.639	.639	.639	.639

The values of Skewness and Kurtosis of pre-test and post-test scores of self-efficacy of experimental and control groups show that the variables, except for post-test scores of self-efficacy of control group, are approximately normally distributed. Post-test scores of self-efficacy of control group are found to be leptokurtic.

Test of Significance For Difference Between Means of Pre-Test Scores of Self-Efficacy of Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 2 Test of significance for the difference between means of Pre-test scores of self-efficacy of the Control group and Experimental group

Group	N	Mean	SD	C.R.	Level of significance
Control group	54	75.07	6.8	1.61	Not significant
Experimental group	54	72.87	7.38		

Table 2 reveals that the critical ratio obtained is 1.61 and insignificant at 0.05 levels. It indicates no significant difference in Pre-test scores of Self-efficacy of the Control and Experimental groups. The Pre-test scores of Self-efficacy of the Control group (M=75.07) and experimental group (M=72.87) are almost equal. Hence it can be concluded that the Pre-test scores of Self-efficacy of the Control group are almost equal to that of the experimental group.

Test of Significance For Difference Between Means of Post-Test Scores of Self-Efficacy of Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 3 Test of significance for the difference between means of Post-test scores of self-efficacy of Control group and Experimental group

Group	N	Mean	SD	C.R.	Level of significance
Control group	54	76.80	6.03	11.18	0.01
Experimental group	54	81.72	4.788		

Table 3 reveals that the critical ratio obtained is 11.18 and is significant at 0.01. It indicates a significant difference in Post-test scores of Self-efficacy of the Control and Experimental groups. The Post-test scores of achievement in commerce of the Control group (M=76.80) and experimental group (M=81.72) significantly differ.

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Hence it can be concluded that the experimental group's post-test scores of self-efficacy is higher than that of the control group

Test of Significance for Difference Between Means Of Post-Test Scores Of Self-Efficacy Of Control Group And Experimental Group Using ANCOVA

Table Test of significance for the difference between means of Post-test scores of self-efficacy of Control group and Experimental group using ANCOVA

Source of variation	df	SSx	SSy	SSxy	SSy.x	MSy.x	F	Level of significance
Among means	1	131.12	655.15	-293.09	1014.9	1014.9	80.9	0.05
Within groups	105	5437.8	3147.59	3154.87	1317.22	12.54		
Total	106	5568.92	3802.74	2861.78	2332.12			

The calculated value of F is 80.9 and is significant at 0.05 level ($F = 80.9$; $p < 0.05$). This shows that the final mean scores of treatment groups differ significantly after they have been adjusted for differences in the pre-test scores of self-efficacy.

Adjusted Means of Post-Test Scores of Self-Efficacy of Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 5 Adjusted means of Post-test scores of self-efficacy of Control group and Experimental group

Groups	Number of students	Pre-test	Post-test	Adjusted Post-test	SEd between adjusted means	t value
Control group	54	75.07	76.8	76.16	.673	9.212
Experimental group	54	72.87	81.72	82.36		

The obtained t value is 9.21, which is significant at 0.01 level. The significant difference between the adjusted post-test means indicates that the pupils of experimental and control groups differ significantly in their post-test scores of self-self-efficacy after they have been adjusted for difference in the pre-test scores of self-efficacy. Since the adjusted mean of the experimental group is significantly greater than that of the control group, the experimental group is superior to the control group in post-test self-efficacy scores.

Conclusion

The investigator found that the Pre-test self-efficacy scores of the Control group are almost equal to that of the experimental group. The experimental group's post-test self-efficacy scores are significantly higher than the control groups. Hence it can be concluded that the Self-directed Learning Package effectively enhances the Self-efficacy of higher secondary school students. Self-directed learning teaches pupils the abilities they will need to manage real-world projects, organize a gazillion tasks, and address problems that arise in everyday life. The student gains independence and mastery from SDL, and the educational process gains a sense of direction. Self-directed learning promotes self-efficacy, which is the belief in one's ability to control one's motivation, behaviour, and social environment. Self-efficacy is the belief that we control the circumstances that affect our lives.

References

- [1] Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191–215. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295x.84.2.191>
- [2] Bandura, A. (1994). Self-efficacy [Electronic version]. In VS Ramachandran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of human behavior* (Vol. 4, pp. 71-81). New York, NY: Academic Press
- [3] Baron, R. S & Byrne. (2004). *Social Psychology*. Jakarta: Erlangga .
- [4] Basereh, N., & Pishkar, K. (2016). Self-directed learning and self-efficacy belief among Iranian EFL learners at the advanced level of language proficiency. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 3(1), 232-240.

- [5] Basri, H. (1996). *Qualified Youth: Adolescent problems & solutions*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- [6] Boyer, N. R., & Usinger, P. (2015). Tracking pathways to success: triangulating learning success factors. *International Journal of Self-Directed Learning*, 12(2), 22-48.
- [7] Brockett, R. G., & Hiemstra, R. (2018). *Self-direction in adult learning: Perspectives on theory, research, and practice*. Routledge.
- [8] Brookfield, S. D. (2009). *International handbook of education for the changing world of work*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5281-1_172
- [9] Grover, K. (2015). Online social networks and the self-directed learning experience during a health crisis. *Int. J. Self Direct. Learn*, 12, 1-15.
- [10] Hamalik, O. (2010). *Teaching and learning process*. Jakarta: PT. Earth Literacy.
- [11] Hendricson, W. D., Andrieu, S. C., Chadwick, D. G., Chmar, J. E., Cole, J. R., George, M. C., Glickman, G. N., Glover, J. F., Goldberg, J. S., Haden, N. K., Meyerowitz, C., Neumann, L., Pyle, M., Tedesco, L. A., Valachovic, R. W., Weaver, R. G., Winder, R. L., Young, S. K., & Kalkwarf, K. L. (2006). Educational strategies associated with development of problem-solving, critical thinking, and self-directed learning. *Journal of Dental Education*, 70(9), 925–936. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.0022-0337.2006.70.9.tb04163.x>
- [12] Kaufman, D. M. (2003). Applying educational theory in practice. *Br. Med. J.* 326, 213–216. doi: 10.1136/bmj.326.7382.213
- [13] Knowles, M. S. (1975). *Self-directed learning: A guide for learners and teachers*. Cambridge, The Adult Education Co., c1975.
- [14] Knowles, M. S. (1993). *Self-directed learning: A guide for learners and teachers*. Granary Press.
- [15] Luszczynska, A., & Schwarzer, R. (2020). Changing behavior using social cognitive theory. *The Handbook of Behavior Change*, 32–45. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108677318.003>

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

ISLAM AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Introduction

Associate Professor and Head, PG and Research Department of Economics, Jamal Mohamed College, Trichy. Inclusive education is defined as a system of learning which includes everyone and one that can cater to the learning needs of Children with Disabilities. Inclusive education aims at transforming the education system by eliminating barriers that can hinder every student to participate fully in education. Such barriers are arising from ethnicity, gender, social status, poverty and others. In other words, inclusive education is, thus, education of children with special needs which are educated with other children (normal) to optimize the potential. According to UNESCO (2004), Inclusive education is the core of the human right to education. The logical consequence of this right is that all children have the right to receive the kind of education that does not discriminate against the background of disability, ethnicity, religion, language, gender, capabilities, culture, and other conditions. The Declaration of Human Rights 1948 states that “everyone has the right to education”. It means that everyone including people with disabilities both men and women have the right to a proper education without discrimination. Thus the right to education is a human right. People with disabilities have been facing challenges from society’s misconceptions, and prejudices in many different ways. United States of America enacted the Education for All Handicapped Children Act (Public Law 94-142) in 1975. This law ensured that all children with disabilities had the opportunity to receive a free appropriate public education in the “least restrictive environment.” The law has since been revised many times over the years. According to the American Congress held in 2004 “Disability is a natural part of the human experience and in no way diminishes the right of individuals to participate in or contribute to society. Improving educational results for children with disabilities is an essential element of our national policy of ensuring equality of opportunity, full participation, independent living, and economic self-sufficiency for individuals with disabilities.” Inclusion means being included in life and participating using one’s abilities in day to day activities as a member of the community. Thus Inclusion can occur in schools, communities, religious activities, playgrounds, work, and recreation.

Islam and Disabled People

Islam opposes prejudice against and exclusion of any group of people. In Quran it is revealed by Almighty that He created us from one man and one woman meaning then that we are all equal and that all human beings are created through the same process, not in a manner in which some are created better than others. Fethullah Gulen says, “Islam promotes equality as the will of God Almighty and requires mutual respect of fellow human beings. Islam embraces every individual and every group with the same equality and warmth. To illustrate Islamic attitudes towards people with disabilities, the verses from Holy Quran, and the life example of Prophet Muhammad and his sayings, which are called hadith can be referred. In one of the hadith, Prophet Mohamed said, “God the Merciful, shows mercy to Merciful people. Show mercy to those on earth so that God shows mercy on you”. It is the duty and responsibility of everyone to serve the needs of others, and Divine mercy and blessings will be showered on us. Islamic history has a shining record of many examples of people who, while having some kind of disability, were included and had prominent status in society. Prophet Muhammad appointed one of his companions by the name of Abdullah Ibn Umm Maktoom, who was blind, as a caller for prayer, and asked him to lead the city of Medina when the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) had to travel outside.

Inclusive Education in Islamic Perspectives

Islam teaches values that can be treated as the basis of education for the people including the disabled people. According to Santoso (2005) there are tangency points between inclusive education and Islamic teachings. Education as a liability / rights, the principle of non-segregation, holistic perspective of looking at learners and way of looking at the barriers that are more oriented to external factors, especially the school environment are the tangency points.

Education as a Liability / Right

In the teachings of Islam, seeking knowledge is obligatory for both men and women. This is in accordance with the words of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), “Seeking knowledge is obligatory for every

Muslim” and “Acquire knowledge, even if you must go to China for it.” These sayings shows the importance of education for every Muslim both men and women, young or old. Likewise, people with disabilities, they also have the same right to obtain a proper education like other normal children. In the perspective of inclusion, education is a human right. Welfare governments have an obligation to cater the educational needs of all citizens including those with disabilities. Thus, Islam and inclusive education equally stressed the importance of studying obligations.

Principle of Non-Segregation

The implied meaning of Inclusive education is education as a human right. The Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) directed Muslims to not only gather knowledge, but also to pass it on for wider benefit of the people. Every human being should not be isolated and marginalized in obtaining educational services. Islam emphasizes that there should be no discrimination in acquiring knowledge. Thus both Islam and inclusive education establishes the fact that education is for all.

Holistic Perspective of Looking at Learners

Islamic education and inclusive education advocate that education should develop the talents, skills and the potential of learners different from each other and form a good personality. Prophet Muhammad (SAW) made it clear in his sayings that knowledge not used for benefit was indeed no knowledge.

The Way of Looking at the Barriers

External factors such as the school environment have an important role in creating a conducive learning atmosphere. If the school cannot create a conducive environment then this may impede the learning process proportionally. An environment that meets the needs of all learners including those with disabilities is essential. Sachar committee report on minority affairs found that lack of hostel facilities, non-availability of public schools in nearest places are the reasons for 4% Muslim students who opted for madaras education. From the above points it can be inferred that in the perspective of Islam, inclusive education should provide educational services to the people without distinction of physical form, ethnicity, race, religion and others. Through religious education, the students with disabilities can have the spiritual power of religion, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills needed for him, and also for the society.

Conclusion

People with disabilities are part of our society and have their rights to participate fully and equally in all kinds of activities. Through an inclusive education children with disabilities can become an active member of society. Meeting all their needs together increases their ability to achieve academic and physical growth which improves their overall quality of life and social status. The formal education sector should be no longer a social divider that distinguishes people with disabilities with the general public. Therefore, the educational system has to provide a balanced education between the intellectual, emotional and spiritual. This requires professional and qualified teachers and educators, a good school management, modified curriculum, appropriate activities and teaching methods, educational facilities and community empowerment.

References

- [1] Inclusive education for children with disabilities during COVID-19-DR KIRTHIKA RAJARAMAN, NIVEDITA KRISHNA
- [2] INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: THE ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE International Journal of Islamic Studies Volume 4, Issue 1, February 2016 Sri Wahyuningsih STAIN Kudus, Central Java, Indonesia.
- [3] Santoso, Fattah (2005). “School of Shari’ah and inclusive education”. National Seminar Papers and launch of Shariah school curriculum and guide the implementation of the inclusive education of UNESCO, UNS.
- [4] People with disabilities from an Islamic perspective: Hurisa Guvercin, fountainmagazine.com

EDUCATION FOR WOMEN'S EQUALITY: INDIAN SCENARIO

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Abstract

Educated women can play a very important role in the development of the country. Women education in India has a major preoccupation of both the government and civil society. Education is milestone of women empowerment because it enables them to responds to the challenges, to confront their traditional role and change their life. So that we can't neglect the importance of education in reference to women empowerment and India poised to becoming superpower in recent years. Education of women is the most powerful tool to change the position in society. Women education in India has been a need of the hour, as education is a foundation stone for the empowerment of woman. Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family and develops the concept of participation.

Keywords: *Education, Women's equality*

Introduction

Education for Women's Equality is a vital component of the overall strategy of securing equity and social justice. *Inter alia*, they emphasize the provision of special support services and removal of factors which result in discrimination against women at all levels of education. The Programme of Action (POA) clearly spells out the actions which need to be taken to promote education for women's equality: it can hardly be improved upon. What is sought to be done is to modify the contents of the POA wherever appropriate. What comes out clearly is the need for will to implement and institutional mechanisms to ensure that gender sensitivity is reflected in the implementation of educational programmes across the board, Education for Women's Equality is too important to be left to the individual commitments or proclivities of persons in charge of implementing programmes. It should be incumbent on all actors, agencies and institutions in the field of education at all educational programmes and activities. An over-whelming proportion of vocational, higher and technical educational facilities are located in urban or semi-urban areas. Participation of girls in this sector continues to be low and gender stereotyped. Similarly, proportion of women and girls in engineering and agriculture based courses is woefully low. This is compounded by the fact that the proportion of women teacher in the low literacy States is extremely poor. It is therefore imperative that the entire educational system is alive to the gender and regional dimensions of educational disparities.

Empowerment of Women

Education can be an effective tool for women's empowerment the parameters of which are:

- 1) enhance self esteem and self confidence of women;
- 2) building a positive image of women by recognizing their contribution to the society, polity and the economy;
- 3) developing ability to think critically;
- 4) fostering decision making and action through collective processes;
- 5) enable women to make informed choices in areas like education, employment and health (especially reproductive health);
- 6) ensuring equal participation in developmental processes;
- 7) providing information, knowledge and skill for economic independence;
- 8) enhancing access to legal literacy and information relating to their rights and entitlements in society with a view to enhance their participation on an equal footing in all areas;

The following measures will be taken for achievement of the above parameters and the concerned bureaus and institutions will report on progress as:

- 1) Every educational institution will take up active programmes of women's development;
- 2) All teachers and instructors will be trained as agents of women's empowerment. Training programmes will be developed by NCERT, NIEPA, DAE, SRCs, D1ETs, SCERTs and the university system. Innovative training programmes will be designed with the assistance of concerned organizations and women's groups;
- 3) Gender and poverty sensitization programmes will be developed for teacher educators and administrators. An environment will be created whereby all the sections of the education sector

- will become alive and sensitive to the role of education in eliminating gender disparities.
- 4) In order to create a greater confidence and to motivate parents to send girls to schools, preference will be given to recruitment of women teachers.
 - 5) The common core curriculum is a potentially powerful instrument to promote a positive image of women. The Department of Women's Studies, NCERT will intensify activities already initiated in the area of developing gender sensitive curriculum, removing sex bias from textbooks and training of trainers/teachers. SCERT and the concerned State level boards and institutions will initiate similar work.
 - 6) Funds would require to be earmarked in all education budgets for such awareness and advocacy related activities.

Research and Women's Studies

Women's Studies is a critical input to promote better understanding of women's contribution to social processes within social, technological and environmental change, their struggles and aspirations, conceptual obstacles that make them "invisible" in many areas of scientific enquiry. The programme aims to investigate and remove structural, cultural or attitudinal causes of gender discrimination, and thus empower women to achieve effective participation in all areas of national or international development. The four dimensions to be supported are:

- 1) Research to advance the frontiers of knowledge develops human resources and produce teaching/learning material in pursuit of the above aims.
- 2) Teaching to change present attitudes and values of men and women to one of concern for gender equality. Existing biases and deficiencies in curriculum will be addressed.
- 3) Training of teachers, decision makers, administrators and planners to enable them to play a positive interventionist role for gender equality.
- 4) Extension or direct involvement of institutions in women's development activities among the community.

Networking between different institutions for research, extension and information dissemination has demonstrated high cost-effectiveness as well as potential for coordinated growth. Such networks will be initiated to increase output of quality teaching materials especially in regional languages, training and curriculum design, and decentralized area-specific models of intervention. Foundation course should be designed and introduced for undergraduates with a view to promote the objectives of empowerment of women.

Universalization of Elementary Education for the Girl Child

It is impossible to achieve Universal Elementary Education (UEE) unless concerted efforts are made to reach out to the girl child. Girls who cannot attend formal schools or have had to drop out will be provided educational opportunities through Non-Formal Education (NFE). Efforts will be made to design special NFE programmes for out-of-school and adolescent girls with a view to get them back into the formal stream or qualify for technical or vocational education. Open School, distance education systems and other innovative educational programmes will reach out to girls in rural remote areas and urban slums. Voluntary and community based effort will be encouraged in this sector. The above tasks acquire a greater significance in the SAA RC decade of the girl child.

The rural girls are doubly disadvantaged by non availability of educational facilities and by the work they have to do related with fuel, fodder, water, sibling care and paid and unpaid work. Coordinated efforts, albeit with other Departments/Ministers, need to be made to provide the necessary support services to enhance their participation and performance. Provision of support services & child care facilities should be seen as a necessary and integral adjunct of UEE

An important constraining factor for female education is the lack of women teachers in rural areas. The Revised Policy Formulations postulate that at least 50 per cent of teachers recruited in future would be women. Therefore special efforts would be made to recruit women teachers and to augment teacher-training facilities for women so that adequate number of qualified women teachers are available in different subjects, including Mathematics and Science.

Total Literacy Campaigns (TLCs) being taken up should pay special attention to women in the 15-35 age group as it has been done with very positive impact in many districts. NFE should be dovetailed to TLCs in order to reach out to girls in the 10-20 age groups. Programmes for continuing education should be designed to ensure that neo-literates and school going girls have access to reading materials. If necessary, books and

magazines should be made available to women in their hamlets. The medium of radio will be utilized to sustain enthusiasm and motivation. Efforts should be made to coordinate the different vocational schemes both within the formal system and those initiated by other Departments/Ministries.

Women's Access to Vocational, Technical and Professional and location and Existing and Emergent Technologies

Improvement of girls' access to technical, vocational and professional education requires a national programme to introduce and strengthen Science and Mathematics teaching in the girls schools. A special scheme will be designed to meet the shortfall of Science and Mathematics teachers in girl's school. Serious efforts should be made by the Centre and State planner curriculum developers and administrators to consciously encourage participation of girls in non-tradition and emergent technologies at all levels. Guidance and counselling for girls should be undertaken as a necessary precondition to encourage participation. Women's access to technical education will be improved qualitatively and quantitatively especially in rural areas. Women's ITIs and Polytechnics and women's wings in general Polytechnics and ITIs will be revamped with a view to diversify disciplines, trades and courses to encourage participation in new and emerging technologies. Information about credit, banking, entrepreneurial abilities will be developed in technical and vocational institutions. The apprenticeship scheme will be strengthened to increase the coverage of women.

Media

The electronic, print and traditional media will be used to create a climate for equal opportunities for women and girls. It will thus play a complementary and supportive role in awareness generation, dissemination of information and communication. Given the fact that almost all rural areas are covered by radio, special efforts will be made to utilize this medium to reach out to women.

Management Structure at Central and State Level

Women's cells should be set up forthwith in all Centre and State agencies concerned with curriculum development, training and research. A Monitoring cell will be set up within the Planning Bureau of the Department of Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development. Similar units in the states should take responsibility for monitoring and evaluating progress. A high level Inter Ministerial Committee will be constituted by the Department of Education, MHRD. Similar committees will be constituted at the State level.

Conclusion

Women play an imperative role in making a nation progressive and guide it towards development. They are essential possessions of a lively humanity required for national improvement, so if we have to see a bright future of women in our country, giving education to them must be a pre-occupation. The education of women is the most powerful tool to change the position of society. Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family. To encourage the education of women at all levels and for dilution of gender bias in providing knowledge and education, established schools, colleges and universities even exclusively for women in the state. The education develops the idea of participation in government, panchayats, public matters etc for elimination of gender discrimination.

References

- [1] Agarwal, M. (2013). Women Empowerment and Gender Equality. New Delhi: Kanishka Publishers.
- [2] Publishers.
- [3] Khan, M.I & Sharma, S.R (2007). Equality and Education: With Special Reference to Women. New Delhi: Kanishka Publishers.
- [4] <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1081705.pdf>

CONSEQUENCE OF BULGARIAN BAG TRAINING ON LEG STRENGTH AND ARM STRENGTH AMONG MALE CRICKET PLAYERS

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Abstract

This paper describes the impact of Bulgarian bag training among cricketers. It's also explains how a cricketer's leg strength and arm strength can be improved by doing this type of training. Also this topic describes how to practice the Bulgarian back drill. For this research cricket players with minimum three years of experience were selected from Tiruchirappalli district and their average age was 18 to 25. They were divided into two experimental group and control group each group consists of fifteen subjects. Group I underwent Bulgarian bag training , Group II underwent control group. Pre and Post tests were conducted on the leg strength and arm strength. The collected data were statistically analyzed by (ANCONA) to determine the significance difference,if any,between the groups. A confidence level of 0.05 was set to test the level of significance different,if any between the groups. The results proved that the Bulgarian bag training group was significantly better in improving the leg strength and arm strength than the control group.

Introduction

Bulgarian Bag Training was created in 2005 by Bulgarian wrestling coach Ivan Ivanov. Its also known as banana bag training . Due to the lack of adequate training equipment in Bulgaria, he developed this training for the wrestling training of his athletes. This exercise is currently one of the most popular and influential in the world of sports and fitness. It's help to developed grip strengthens and increases muscular endurance of wrists, arms, shoulders, back, legs and rotator cuff muscles. It helps improve core muscles, coordination and overall shoulder and joint mobility. This exercise is very popular because it is different from other exercises. Bulgarian bag are made of leather and canvas and bags made of it are filled with soil. It weight starting from 5 kg to 24 kg.

Benefits of Bulgarian Bag

- 1) Help to develop grip strength
- 2) Increase muscular endurance of wrist
- 3) Improve core muscles
- 4) Its help to develop leg and arm strength.
- 5) Over all development of shoulder and joint mobility.
- 6) Development of coordination.

Strength: The ability to exert force in order to overcome the resistance

Leg strength : Leg strength, the ability to exert force with the lower extremities quickly.

Arm Strength: Maximum velocity of any throw made by a fielder

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Bulgarian bag training on leg strength and arm strength among male cricket players.

Hypothesis

- 1) It was hypothesized that there would be a significant improvement on leg strength and arm strength due to the Bulgarian bag training among male cricket players.
- 2) It was hypothesized that there would be a better significant improvement on leg strength and arm strength due to Bulgarian bag training among male cricket players .

Review of Related Literature

Vairavasundara, Dr. A. Palanisamy (March 2015) Effect of Bulgarian bag training on selected physical variables among hand ball players.The purpose of the study was find out the effect of Bulgarian bag training

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among hand ball players. Age of the subject between 18 to 25 and also the subject had experience at least 3 years in handball and only who has represented intercollegiate level tournament they are selected as a subject for this study. Totally , thirty (N=30) handball players randomly selected from Bharadidasan University affiliated colleges Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu. The subject are divided into two groups . Group-I Experimental Group (Bulgarian Bag Training Group), Group-II Control Group.Physical test were performed by each participant. Its include leg power, muscles strength and flexibility leg explosive power assessed by standing broad jump, muscle strength assessed by push-ups,flexibility assessed by sit and reach. The subject were randomly assigned into two group each fifteen as experimental group control group. The experimental group performed 3 alternate days in a weak, one session per day, and Bulgarian bag training each session lasted 60 minutes foe 8 weeks. The control group maintain their daily routine activities no special training was given .Experimental group and control subject were tested on selected variables before and after training period.The collected data were statistically analyzed by (ANCONA) to determine the significance difference,if any,between the groups. A confidence level of 0.05 was set to test the level of significance different,if any between the groups.

Methodology

Selectiono Subjects

To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty (N=30) male-Cricket players have been randomly selected from Tiruchirappalli District ,Tamil Nadu, India. The age of subjects were ranged from 18 to 25 years. The subjects had experience of at least three Years in cricket and only who has represented in the District level tournament were taken as subjects. The following variables are selected as criterion variables such as Leg strength, and Arm strength. Leg strength assessed by standing broad jump, arm strength assessed by push- ups The subjects were randomly assigned Into two groups of fifteen each, such as and control experimental groups. The experimental group participated in the Bulgarian bag training for 4 alternative days in a week, one Session per day and for 6 weeks each session lasted 60 Minutes. The control group maintained their daily routine Activities and no special training was given. The subjects Of the two groups were tested on selected variables prior And immediately after the training period.

Selection of Variables

Independent Variables

- 1) Bulgarian Bag Training

Dependent Variable

- 1) Leg Strength
- 2) Arm Strength

Staistical Technique

The collected Data were analyzed statistically through analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) to find out the significance difference, if Any between the groups. The 0.05 level of confidence was Fixed to test the level of significance difference.

Table - I

S.NO	Criterion Measure	Test items	Unit of measurement
1	Leg strength	Standing broad jump	In meters
2	Arm strength	Push- up	In numbers

Table-II Analysis Of Leg Strength And Arm Strength Among Control Group And Bulgarian Bag Training Groups

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S.NO	Variables	Group	Pre- test mean	SD	Post-Test mean	SD	Adjusted mean
1	Leg strength	CG	1.52	.2829	1.50	.272	1.527
		BBTG	1.56	.3130	1.89	.343	1.862
2	Arm strength	CG	27.44	0.30	29.30	1.36	29.33
		BBTG	27.28	0.22	30.67	1.15	30.65

BBTG - Bulgarian bag training group

CG- Control Group

The table II the pre- test and post -test means, standard deviation and adjusted means on leg strength and arm strength of male cricket players were numerical presented. The analysis of co-variance on selected variables of Bulgarian Bag Training Group and Control Group presented in table- III

Table - III Analysis of Covariance

Significant at 0.05 level of confidences

S.NO	Variables	Test	Sum of variance	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F ratio
1	Leg strength	Pre test	Between group	0.042	1	0.042	0.58
			With in groups	1.574	22	0.072	
		Post test	Between groups	26.686	1	26.686	7.22
			With in groups	81.062	22	3.685	
		Adjusted means	Between group	26.949	1	26.949	7.00
			With in groups	80.731	21	3.844	
2	Arm strength	Pre test	Between group	0.141	1	0.141	1.99
			With in groups	1.552	22	0.071	
		Post test	Between group	11.144	1	11.144	7.01
			With in groups	34.945	22	1.588	
		Adjusted means	Between group	9.547	1	9.547	5.75
			With in groups	34.809	21	1.658	

In the table the results of analysis of covariance on leg strength and arm strength. The obtained 'F' ratio of 0.58, 1.99 for Pre -test means was less than the table value of 4.30 for df 1 and 22 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence on leg strength and arm strength. The obtained 'F' ratio of 7.22, 7.01 for post-test means was greater than the table value of 4.30 for df 1 and 22 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence on leg strength arm strength. The obtained 'F' ratio of 7.00, 5.75 for adjusted post-test means was greater than the table value of 4.33 for df 1 and 21 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence on leg strength and arm strength. The result of the study indicated that there was a significant difference among the adjusted post test means of Bulgarian bag training with Bulgarian bag training group and control group on leg strength and arm strength. And also Bulgarian bag training with Bulgarian bag training group showed significant improvement on leg strength and arm strength compared to control group.

Conclusion

From the analysis of data, the following conclusion were drawn. The experimental group cricket players showed significant improvement in two variables of leg strength and arm strength. The control group cricket players did not show significant improvement in any selected variables.

Reference

- [1] Connie cook The Retrieved Oct.5, 2010. Bag boy of fitness “ Challenges You With Bulgarian Training bags san diego downtown(Aug 2009)
- [2] C.R.Bino Bijoy , Dhanaraj Sornalingam (Sep 2019). Influence of Bulgarian Bag Training On Selected Strength Parameters And Performance Variables Among Volleyball Players Peer reviewed journal (ISSN-2395-1877)
- [3] Sivakumar.R & Arumugam -(Oct 2019).A Study on the Upshot of Bulgarian Bag Training on Core Strength and Shoulder Strength among Soccer Players(ISSN-2349-5162)
- [4] Antony,B., Maheswri,M.U., & Palanisamy ,A. (2005) Impact of battle rope and Bulgarian bag high intensity interval training protocol on selected strength and physiological variables among school level athletes. IJAR, 1(8), 403-406.

REIMAGING OF EDUCATION IN THE NEW ERA

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Abstract

Educated unemployment is one of the problems of India in regard to social and economic problems. This is a big obstacle in the path of economic development. This is something different kind of unemployment. Any person studying graduation or postgraduation but unemployed is considered as educated unemployed. In India now the day's problem of educated unemployment is in serious form and alarming also. The 8th annual all-India survey on higher education 2018-19 released by the HRD ministry as well as a report by the Center for monitoring Indian economy on "unemployment in India- A statistical profile" for May- august 2019 pointed to a simmering Volcano of educated unemployment. This situation is not only posted COVID-19 pandemic effects but many other reasons. Mushrooming of new universities in the past few years seems to produce only degree holders but not quality education, adding fuel to this fire of educated unemployment. Most of the students with degrees from such universities learn very little in terms of life skills and vocational skills relevant to employability. So the Indian education system is facing both qualitative and quantitative challenges.

Introduction

'Education' plays a significant and remedial role in improving and balancing the country's socio-economic conditions. Today, we are living in a world of paradox. On one hand, science and technology are advancing very fast, while on the other, most of the societies are facing problems such as intolerance, mental illness, stress, crime, corruption, egoism, drug abuse and unemployment name a few. Human behaviour becomes hollow and education becomes directionless with less employability maybe the reason is lack of quality education, education without values and lack of vocational skills. A study by Edutech and skill development company has found that 53% educated youth in India are unemployed due to lack of feature skills. The survey was conducted with over 1100 participants including 141 corporates and provides a deeper insight into India's skill gap and challenges. Some of the key findings from the skill gaps survey : 31% of the survey's participants declared that their existent degree failed in providing them with future skills. Over 53% also confessed that they were unable to find the job of their choice. 60% admitted they were not earning the ideal salary after duly completing their degree. Almost 70% said that training in futuristic skills could have helped them in bolstering their professional career (reported in India Today web desk 18 Sept 2021). India's skill development quotient needs a desperate upheaval and strategies and it is also a focus area as per the new NEP -2020. NEP-2020 lays particular emphasis on the development of the each individual, holistic development with not only higher order cognitive capacities but also social ethical and emotional capabilities. Special emphasis is also laid upon life skills which over youth lacks like communication skills, co-operation, teamwork, resilience in specific developing emotional quotient, social quotient, moral quotient and above all adversity quotient, entrepreneurial mind-set and skills specially keeping in view adversity faced by human community due to pandemic covid-19 resulting in depression, suicides, domestic violence, mental illness and above all economic crisis as mass level layoff happened. Secondly, to create the needed vocational skills our system requires reimagination of 'education.' Collaborative Intelligence will come to the force wherein humans and technology will join forces. Artificial Intelligence is depth and scale to newer challenges and so humans have to acquire and cultivate skills to compliment technology. The future education system will have to be very different as known today. It is assumed that upto 2030, skill based and artificial technology enabled education would be a game- changer. Innovation of chatbot (chat GPT) is like the invention of electricity, printing press, automobile etc. Open AI based chatbot can develop not only clear, continuous and relevant material of different subjects but also right reports, analyse complex topics, synthesize different research findings and can suggest new areas and research topics. Now, machines are in the role of creator which was also the domain power of the human brain till now.

INTERNET USAGE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THANJAVUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

Internet is the most wanted information and communication technology that brought the worldwide revolutionary change in the information scenario. It helps students to broaden their academic knowledge, research and assignments by accessing to the information world and also by easy communication to their academic community. Though there are many benefits linked with Internet use, there has been a growing concern regarding the risk associated with Internet overuse. It is reported that Internet has a significant decrement onto students' achievement. This study aimed to determine the association between Internet usage and Academic Performance of higher secondary school students in a Thanjavur District. Survey method of research was used. A sample of 200 students was selected from different higher secondary schools of Thanjavur District through Simple Random sampling technique. The self developed Internet Usage and Academic Performance questionnaire was used to collect the data. It was found that all the students irrespective of their Internet Usage and Academic Performance. The result of the research is that there is no significance in Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students of Gender, Subject and Types of Institution. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students of Locality. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

Keywords: *Internet Usage, Academic Performance and Secondary School Students*

Introduction

The population explosion and explosion of knowledge are not only affecting the pattern of human life, but also inflict their impact on education. The population is increasing in geometrical proportion and new frontiers of knowledge are being opened up almost daily. The explosion of population and knowledge has raised the serious question of both quality and quantity of education. Education is of the opinion that the educational problems relating to quantity and quality could be talked by the development of educational technology. Therefore, there has seen a rapid development of communication technology in education facilities and upgrading instructions. The World Wide Web and the internet offer new horizons to reach, modern global audience. The internet is the largest province for researchers and academics in laboratories, offices, classrooms and homes. Now, the internet is everywhere, it is growing rapidly worldwide. It also provides teachers and students a guide for hands – on experiments with the internet.

Need and Significance of the Study

Teaching learning practices are evolving day by day in higher education with emphasis being shifted to student's centric learning. Various efforts being put into practice to use internet usage to harness effective learning. As younger generations are using such technology in the classrooms, they remark the educational landscape. For the learning and teaching in the recent years academics have been expanding their internet usage to offer after hours, support for students. The use of internet will enhance learning, increase participation and engagement, improve content dissemination and improve pedagogy and information sharing.

Review of Related Literature

The investigator reviewed the following research studies. Nalwa and Anand (2003) highlighted the negative impact of Internet on Students Academic Performance. The present study is intended to study the impact of Internet on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students. Park and Choi (2007) found that Boys students use more internet than Girls students. There are a number of studies on the Internet usage among Boys and Girls students. Despite the gender equality and constitutional safe guards of the Girls, the Boys dominated the Internet Usage in Secondary School Students. Judd and Kennedy (2010) found the use of the internet saves time and enhances the academic performance of students. The Internet provides huge information on real time basis. It is the easiest and the chief source of information among studies. Students show high percentage of internet users as

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compared to general secondary school students. Pardhasardhi and Goel (2015) studied the influence of access use of internet on academic performance of adolescents. The data was analyzed using method of descriptive statistics and the finding revealed that the internet was useful for education and it had a positive influence on students Academic Performance. Mir and Paray (2018) studied the Internet usage and Academic Performance of Higher Secondary School Students in Kashmir. The study found significant difference between the Academic Performance scores of Internet user and non-users students, where the internet users performed well in academic score as compare to the non-users.

Statement of the Problem

The twenty first century of is the world of technology where most of the people do not even imagine their life without internet. Modern technology in communication has no doubt turned the complete world into a “Global Community”. It helps individuals to be better learned open mind and keeping informed with global growth. Internet discloses humanity to a better way of doing things. Even our days start with alarm in mobile phone and end with what’s an app message on the smart phone, this situation is prevailing even in most of the rural areas. Using technology in the classroom has two sides, same as coins both positive as well as negative. So the investigator decided to take up the research study on Internet Usage and Academic Performance among Higher Secondary School Students.

Objectives of the Study

- 1)To find the level of Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students.
- 2)To study the difference in Internet Usage in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 3)To study the difference in Academic Performance in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 4)To find out the relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students

Hypothesis of the Study

- 1) There is no significant difference in Internet Usage in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 2) There is no significant difference in Academic Performance in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- 3) There is significant relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students.

Methodology of the Study

The Normative survey method is adopted for the study. The variables used are the Internet Usage and Academic Performance. Population: Higher Secondary School Students in Thanjavur District are the population of this study. Sample: The sample consists of 200 higher secondary school students from both Government and Matriculation school in Thanjavur District. Tools: Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school student’s questionnaire was used. The inventory contains 27 & 20 objective items. This was a self developed tool. Validity and Reliability of the Tool: The sample reliability is established by test-retest method by the investigator and the reliability co-efficient in found to be 0.71. Hence the tools are highly reliable. The validity of the test was assessed on the basis of the judgment of the experts. Procedure of Data Collection: The Internet Usage and Academic Performance Questionnaire will be given to the selected sample with a request to fill in the required data enclosing a copy of permission letter from the school Head Master.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

Table-I: Mean and SD of variable Internet Usage and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Internet Usage	200	14.87	5.87

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Boys	102	12.14	4.66
Girls	98	13.02	4.78
Rural	97	12.37	3.92
Urban	103	13.42	4.71
Arts	99	12.45	3.97
Science	101	13.76	4.46
Government School	96	13.33	4.69
Matriculation School	104	12.87	3.21

Table-II: Mean and SD of variable Academic Performance and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Academic Performance	200	12.87	4.56
Boys	102	11.67	3.21
Girls	98	11.87	3.33
Rural	97	11.54	3.54
Urban	103	12.14	3.87
Arts	99	11.68	3.10
Science	101	12.10	3.91
Government School	96	12.13	3.96
Matriculation School	104	11.87	3.03

Differential Analysis

Internet Usage

Table-III: Mean, SD and 't' value of Internet Usage and its sub-variables

Variable	Values			t	S
	No.	Mean	SD		
Boys	102	12.14	4.66	1.58	NS
Girls	98	13.02	4.78		
Rural	97	12.37	3.92	1.99	S
Urban	103	13.42	4.71		
Arts	99	12.45	3.97	1.63	NS
Science	101	13.76	4.46		
Government School	96	13.33	4.69	1.72	NS
Matriculation School	104	12.87	3.21		

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Academic Performance

Table-IV: Mean, SD and 't' value of Academic Performance and its sub-variables

Variable	Values			t	s
	No.	Mean	SD		
Boys	102	11.67	3.21	1.66	NS
Girls	98	11.87	3.33		
Rural	97	11.54	3.54	2.10	S
Urban	103	12.14	3.87		
Arts	99	11.68	3.10	1.73	NS
Science	101	12.10	3.91		
Government School	96	12.13	3.96	1.82	NS
Matriculation School	104	11.87	3.03		

Correlation Analysis

Table-V

Variable	Values		
	No.	'r'	S
Internet Usage and Academic Performance	200	0.132	S
Boys	102	0.121	S
Girls	98	0.102	S
Rural	97	0.012	NS
Urban	103	0.021	NS
Arts	99	0.130	S
Science	101	0.117	S
Government School	96	0.115	S
Matriculation School	104	0.108	S

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

Findings

Descriptive Analysis

Internet Usage: The level of Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students is moderate. Mean score of Girls is higher than the Boys on Internet Usage in higher secondary school students. Mean score of urban school students Internet Usage is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students. The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Internet Usage. The students studying in government higher secondary school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Internet Usage.

Academic Performance: The level of Academic Performance in higher secondary school students is moderate. Mean score of Girls Academic Performance is higher than the Boys in higher secondary school students. Mean score of urban school students Academic Performance is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students. The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Academic Performance. The students studying in government school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation school with respect to Academic Performance.

Differential Analysis

Internet Usage: There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Internet Usage in higher secondary school students. There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Internet Usage in higher secondary school students. There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Internet Usage in higher secondary school students. There is no significant difference between government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Internet Usage in higher secondary school students.

Academic Performance

There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Academic Performance in higher secondary school students. There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Academic Performance in higher secondary school students. There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Academic Performance in higher secondary school students. There is no significant difference between government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Academic Performance in higher secondary school students.

Correlation Analysis

There is a significant relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students. Also there exists significance relationship among Boys, Girls, Arts, Science, Government and Matriculation School. There is no significant relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students with respect to rural and urban.

Suggestions for the Further Research

This study can be extended to high school students and Engineering students. This study is limited only to the selected higher secondary school students in Thanjavur District only and it to be extended to all types of schools and colleges. The present study was carried out during the short period of time with limited samples. The findings and conclusion are needed to be verified larger group size of the samples.

Conclusion

The result of the research is that there is no significance in Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students of Gender, Subject and Types of Institutions. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students of Locality. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

References

- [1] Asan A, Koca N. (2006). Dynamics of internet usage: a case of students of Federal University of Technology Owerri (FUTO) Nigeria. *Educ Res Rev*, 1(6), 192-195.
- [2] Bellamy A, Hanewicz C. (2001). An Exploratory Analyses of the social nature of internet addiction. *Elect J Socio*; ISSN: 1198 3655. Available from URL:
- [3] Chou C, Condrón L, Belland JC. (2005). A review on the research on internet addiction. *Educ Psycho Rev*, 17(4), 363-388. doi:10.10007/s10648-005-8138-1.
- [4] Jones S, Madden M. (2002). *The Internet goes to college: How students are living in the future with today's technology*. Washington, DC: Pew Internet & American Life Project.
- [5] Obedebe PM. (2012). Internet usage and students' academic performance in Nigeria tertiary institutions: a case study of University of Maiduguri, 2(3), 334-343.

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WEBSITE OF EDUCATION APPS IN INDIAN ONLINE LEARNING PLATFORMS: A WEBOMETRICS ANALYSIS

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Abstracts

This paper aims to evaluate the website of Indian online learning apps through the webometrics method. Webometrics is a tool for measuring the impact of the web. 16 Indian online learning platforms are analyzed using the collected data Check PageRank, Similarweb search engine, and other web crawlers. The result found that Byju ranks first with the highest global rank, country rank, and category rank, and Byju with the highest domain authority. Vedantu and Edureka lead with the highest page authority. Adda 247 with got the highest external backlinks. Byju's, my CBSE guide, Vedantu, Toppr, Doubtnut, CAclubindia, Adda 247, Coding Ninjas, Jigsaw academy, and Edureka with very strong PR Quality.

Keywords: *Online Learning Platforms, Global Rank, External Backlinks, PR Quality*

Introduction

Almind & Ingwersen were the ones who initially coined the term "Webometrics" (1997). By measuring the World Wide Web and trying to comprehend its structure and usage patterns, the science of webometrics counts the number of constituent aspects. Webometrics, as defined by (Bjorneborn & Ingwersen 2003), is the study of the quantitative elements of the creation and use of information resource structures and technologies on the web. The 16 Indian online learning app websites chosen for this study were examined from several angles, including global rank, country rank, category rank, domain authority, page authority, external backlinks, and PR quality. This study will aid Indian online learning apps in enhancing the attributes above of their websites in the future for better services. The current research offers website information regarding 16 Indian online learning apps that are exploratory. Table 1 shows the popularity rankings of a few Indian online learning software websites (Muniyasamy et al 2021).

Table – 1: List of selected sample Online Learning Apps websites

S. No	Online Learning Apps	Websites
1	Meritnation	https://www.meritnation.com/
2	Byju's	https://byjus.com/
3	myCBSEGuide	https://mycbseguide.com/
4	Vedantu	https://www.vedantu.com/
5	Vidyakul	https://vidyakul.com/
6	Toppr	https://www.toppr.com/
7	Doubtnut	https://www.doubtnut.com/
8	Drmentors Medical PG app	https://www.drmentors.com/
9	CAclubindia	https://www.caclubindia.com/
10	Indigolearn	https://www.indigolearn.com/
11	Testbook	https://testbook.com/
12	Unacademy	https://unacademy.com/
13	Adda 247	https://www.adda247.com/
14	Coding Ninjas	https://www.codingninjas.com/
15	Jigsaw academy	https://www.jigsawacademy.com/
16	Edureka	https://www.edureka.co/

Review of Literature

Dastani et al. (2019) The Webometrics method was used in this study, which included 41 Websites from Iranian Medical Sciences Universities. For example, Moz, Google, and Google Scholar. The website of the University of Shiraz came out on top. In a nutshell, the findings of this study demonstrated that, except for a small number of universities with high-quality websites, others have little impact. Davydova et al. (2020) In the context of this research, a webometric analysis of 181 national library websites was carried out. The websites of 136 national libraries have been organized into a Global Rank. Their key traffic metrics were examined, and the Internet segments where they could be found were identified. The conclusion has been reached regarding the successful integration of library content into the web environment, the gradual development of web reputation, and the trust rank of specific library websites.

Hadagali et al (2022) The study evaluates the websites of the Indian Institutes of Technology in India using webometric tools and indicators. Simple WIF, self-link WIF, external link WIF, backlinks, and broken links are the parameters used in this study. Tools for collecting data from IIT websites include Google Search Engine, Web Link Analyzer, Back Link Watch, and Broken Link Checker. This research aids in the enhancement of website performance. Such research is beneficial and requires regular updates, editing, and website redesign. People can identify the WIF of websites by using the rankings provided by this study. Brahma and Kumar Verma (2022). The present study will analyze the contents of national library websites in Asia. A Website Optimization tool, Web Page Analyser, was used to analyze the web page size and download speed. In addition, an online tool called Alexa Traffic Rank was used to determine the global ranking of the websites of the selected national libraries.

The study found that the selected national libraries did not keep basic information. As a result, all Asian national libraries should provide all essential information about the library on their website to their users uniformly. Meghwal et al (2022) his study examines the inside of university websites in India ranked NIRF 2021. There was a study analysis of domain age, parameter analysis of web impact factors, and Alexa traffic rank of websites, among other things. Furthermore, it was discovered that all of the university websites made use of various small tools, such as SEO tools. According to the findings, the "Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham" university website has the oldest domain, registered on August 14, 1998, and the "Indian Institute of Science University" website has the highest Domain Authority score of 62, ranking first among all Universities. Furthermore, according to the study, NIRF ranked three Karnataka universities among the top ten universities in India.

Objectives

- 1) To identify the Indian Online Learning Platforms apps websites on the web;
- 2) To discover the domain authority and page authority of the Indian Online Learning Platforms apps websites;
- 3) To count the number of external backlinks of the Indian Online Learning Platforms apps;
- 4) To analyze the global rank, country rank and category rank and PR quality of the Indian Online Learning Platforms apps;
- 5) To analyze the PR quality of the Indian Online Learning Platforms apps;

Methodology

The following methodology has been adopted in this study. The present webometrics study is performed on Indian Online Learning Platforms and app websites (Babu et al 2010).The study data is obtained from 04/12/2022 to 14/12/2022. For this study, search engines and other tools are used. To collect data according to the need and applicability of the research objectives. The data for the websites of Indian Online Learning Platforms apps can be collected by Check PageRank and Similarweb search engine and other web crawlers (Sujithai and Jeyshankar 2013). Therefore, the researcher gets the following data: global rank, country ranking, category ranking, domain authority, page authority, External backlinks, and PR quality. After the data collection, the collected data were analyzed and tabulated, keeping the study's objectives in view. MS excel sheet was used to visualize the network mapping of the websites.

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Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 2. Global Rank of Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	Global Rank	Rank
1	Byju's	356	1
2	Toppr	505	2
3	Vedantu	1599	3
4	Doubtnut	2235	4
5	Testbook	3464	5
6	Unacademy	4268	6
7	Adda 247	6472	7
8	Meritnation	13754	8
9	myCBSEGuide	13804	9
10	Coding Ninjas	18333	10
11	Edureka	26296	11
12	CAclubindia	54025	12
13	Jigsaw academy	128614	13
14	Vidyakul	262764	14
15	Indigolearn	299882	15
16	Drmentors Medical PG app	1577531	16

Table 2 shows the global ranking of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that the Byju is in the top position with (356) ranks, followed by Toppr with (505) ranks second and Vedantu with (1599) ranks, occupying third place globally. The study further observed that the Drmentors Medical PG app (1577531) secured the last position among the 16 Online Learning Apps websites.

Table 3. Country Rank of Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	Country Rank	Rank
1	Byju's	30	1
2	Toppr	46	2
3	Vedantu	134	3
4	Doubtnut	169	4
5	Testbook	275	5
6	Unacademy	329	6
7	Adda 247	470	7
8	myCBSEGuide	985	8
9	Meritnation	1042	9
10	Coding Ninjas	1575	10
11	CAclubindia	3718	11
12	Edureka	3946	12
13	Jigsaw academy	16841	13

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14	Vidyakul	18284	14
15	Indigolearn	21421	15
16	Drmentors Medical PG app	90739	16

Table 3 shows the Country Ranking of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that the Byju, the top position with (30) ranks, followed by Toppr with (46) ranks second, and Vedantu with (134) ranks, occupied third place globally. The study further observed that the Drmentors Medical PG app (90739) secured the last rank among the 16 Online Learning Apps websites.

Table 4. Category Rank of Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	Category Rank	Rank
1	Byju's	1	1
2	Doubtnut	1	
3	Toppr	2	2
4	Adda 247	4	3
5	Vedantu	5	4
6	CAclubindia	11	5
7	Unacademy	11	
8	Testbook	16	6
9	myCBSEGuide	35	7
10	Meritnation	38	8
11	Coding Ninjas	52	9
12	Indigolearn	105	10
13	Edureka	136	11
14	Drmentors Medical PG app	640	12
15	Jigsaw academy	822	13
16	Vidyakul	896	14

Table 4 shows the Category Ranking of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that Byju's and Doubtnut the top position with (1) ranks, followed by Toppr with (2) ranks second and Adda 247 with (4) ranks occupied third places globally. The study further observed that the Vidyakul (896) secured the last rank among the 14 Online Learning Apps websites.

Table 5. Ranking of Domain Authority in Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	Domain Authority	Rank
1	Byju's	62	1
2	Edureka	58	2
3	Toppr	53	3
4	Indigolearn	53	
5	Vedantu	50	4
6	CAclubindia	49	5

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7	Meritnation	47	6
8	Testbook	43	7
9	Adda 247	42	8
10	Jigsaw academy	42	
11	Unacademy	41	9
12	Coding Ninjas	38	10
13	Doubtnut	35	11
14	myCBSEGuide	29	12
15	Vidyakul	24	13
16	Drmentors Medical PG app	14	14

Table 5 shows the Domain Authority of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that Byju's top position with (62) ranks, followed by Edureka with (58) ranks second, and Toppr and Indigolearn with (53) ranks, occupied third places globally. The study further observed that the Drmentors Medical PG app with (14) secured the last rank among the 14 Online Learning Apps websites.

Table 6. Ranking of Page Authority in Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	Page Authority	Rank
1	Vedantu	54	1
2	Edureka	54	
3	Toppr	53	2
4	myCBSEGuide	51	3
5	Adda 247	51	
6	Meritnation	50	
7	CAclubindia	50	4
8	Jigsaw academy	49	5
9	Doubtnut	48	6
10	Coding Ninjas	47	7
11	Unacademy	43	8
12	Vidyakul	43	
13	Byju's	41	9
14	Testbook	35	10
15	Drmentors Medical PG app	32	11
16	Indigolearn	29	12

Table 6 shows the Page Authority of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that Vedantu and Edureka are in the top position with (54) ranks, followed by Toppr with (53) ranks second, and myCBSEGuide and Adda 247 with (51) ranks occupied third places globally. Finally, the study showed that Indigolearn (29) secured the last position among the 12 Online Learning Apps websites.

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Table 7. Ranking of External Backlinks in Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	External Backlinks	Rank
1	Adda 247	5632270	1
2	Edureka	1380431	2
3	CAclubindia	953150	3
4	Vedantu	716864	4
5	Meritnation	632215	5
6	Toppr	351630	6
7	Byju's	65284	7
8	Testbook	63236	8
9	Indigolearn	56356	9
10	Doubtnut	44736	10
11	Unacademy	35241	11
12	Coding Ninjas	31093	12
13	Jigsaw academy	28341	13
14	myCBSEGuide	16444	14
15	Vidyakul	2657	15
16	Drmentors Medical PG app	302	16

Table 7 shows the External Backlinks of Online Learning Apps websites. It is clear from the study that Adda 247 is in the top position with (5632270) ranks, followed by Edureka with (1380431) ranks at second, and CAclubindia with (953150) ranks occupied third places globally.

Table 8. PR Quality in Online Learning Apps

Sl. No	Online Learning Apps	PR Quality
1	Meritnation	Very Strong
2	Byju's	Very Strong
3	myCBSEGuide	Very Strong
4	Vedantu	Very Strong
5	Toppr	Very Strong
6	Doubtnut	Very Strong
7	CAclubindia	Very Strong
8	Adda 247	Very Strong
9	Coding Ninjas	Very Strong
10	Jigsaw academy	Very Strong
11	Edureka	Very Strong
12	Vidyakul	Strong
13	Indigolearn	Strong
14	Drmentors Medical PG app	Moderate
15	Testbook	Moderate

16	Unacademy	Moderate
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Table 8 shows the PR Quality of Online Learning Apps websites. It depicts Meritnation, Byju's, myCBSEGuide, Vedantu, Toppr, Doubtnut, CAclubindia, Adda 247, Coding Ninjas, Jigsaw academy, and Edureka with very strong PR Quality. Vidyakul and Indigolearn, with strong PR Quality, followed him. Drmentors Medical PG app, Testbook, and Unacademy with moderate PR Quality followed him.

Finding

The global rank considered and concluded that Online Learning Apps Byju's, Toppr, and Vedantu websites achieved 1 to 3 positions, and Drmentors Medical PG app website achieved the last positions respectively in both global ranks. The country rank considered and concluded that Online Learning Apps Byju's, Toppr, and Vedantu websites achieved 1 to 3 positions, and Drmentors Medical PG app website achieved the last positions respectively in both country ranks. The category rank considered and concluded that Online Learning App Byju's and Doubtnut, Toppr, and Adda 247 websites achieved 1 to 3 positions, and Vidyakul website achieved the last positions respectively in both category ranks. It is experiential that the Byju's App website achieved the highest domain authority score, 62, with the first position. At the same time, the Drmentors Medical PG app website obtained only the 14 lowest score among respondent domain authorities. Among the Online Learning App websites, the highest page authority scores of 54 is achieved by Vedantu and Edureka websites with the first position. In contrast, the Indigolearn website obtained only 29 lowest scores among respondent page authority. The external backlinks Online Learning App website has the highest external backlinks Score (5632270) scores achieved by Adda 247 website with the first position, whereas Drmentors Medical PG app website scores (302) which is the very lowest score of external backlinks.

Conclusion

The study provides exploratory information on the websites of Indian online learning apps using webometrics methods and gives a good idea of the information they provided. It contains information about their websites' global rank, country rank, category rank, domain authority, page authority, external backlinks, PR quality, and domain names. This ranking can assist administrators of online learning apps in assessing the strengths and weaknesses of their online presence and developing strategies to improve their web presence. In addition, these findings pave the way for further research into other new areas of the web, as well as longitudinal studies to track the changing nature of how communities use the Internet.

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Reference

- [1] Almind, T. C., & Ingwersen, P. (1997). Informetric analyses on the world wide web: methodological approaches to 'webometrics'. *Journal of documentation*, 53(4), 404-426.
- [2] Babu, B. R., Jeyshankar, R., & Rao, P. N. (2010). Websites of Central Universities in India: A webometric analysis. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 30(4), 33-43.
- [3] Björneborn, L., & Ingwersen, P. (2004). Toward a basic framework for webometrics. *Journal of the American society for information science and technology*, 55(14), 1216-1227.
- [4] Brahma, K., & Kumar Verma, M. K. (2022). Web Content Analysis of National Libraries' Websites in Asia: An Evaluation. *International Journal of Information Science and Management (IJISM)*, 20(1).
- [5] Dastani, M., Panahi, S., & Sattari, M. (2019). Webometrics analysis of Iranian universities about medical sciences' websites between September 2016 and march 2017. *Acta Informatica Malaysia (AIM)*, 1(3), 07-12.
- [6] Davydova, I., Marina, O., Marin, S., & Peleshchyshyn, A. (2020). Webometric Analysis of National Libraries Websites. In *COAPSN* (pp. 165-176).

CURIOSITY IS CURSE OR CURE: A CRITICAL STUDY ON H.G. WELLS' THE INVISIBLE MAN

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Abstract

In the fast-growing technological world, people are much allured to scientific inventions and new discoveries. Science plays a vital role in the innovations of human life and their effective existence. As literature opens up a wide gate of inspiration and creativity it also connects the subject of science to explore the unexplored and experience the unseen. Herbert George Wells also known as H. G. Wells is best known for his science fiction novels and he is also called the father of science fiction. Some of his famous works are *The Time Machine* (1895), *The Island of Doctor Moreau* (1896), *The Invisible Man* (1897), *The War of the worlds* (1898) and *The War in the Air* (1907). As a socialist, he is famous for his social criticisms and his science fictions ultimately stood by the test of time. *The Invisible Man* (1897) is a tale about the life and death of a young scientist Griffin who goes mad due to his curiousness. Having gained the knowledge of invisibility he makes himself invisible and uses his invention for nefarious purposes. The novel is a horror and also a fabulous classic that people of all ages enjoy all time. The themes of this novel include isolation, community and scientific advancement the novel also uses various figurative languages and symbols. It is a science fiction with a deep message that has a well-known effect. The message is loud and clear that the medical discovery must be done within social and moral boundaries because failure in doing so might also carry unfavourable effects. This novel could be very particular because it deals with the existence of a scientist who invents a manner to change an object's reflective index to that of air. He invents it because it neither absorbs light nor displays it and consequently will become invisible. For the sake of clarity, he first experiments it on timber, then on a cat and after that he experiments it on himself and goes invisible. However, he does not know how to reverse the technique. It is an adventurous, fascinating and incredible novel that has kept its readers connected throughout. There is not any doubt that this novel is a giant hit with each of the readers and critics.

Keywords: *Science, Invention, Curiosity, Greediness, Crime, Selfish, Society, Fear, Horror, Death*

In the fast-growing technological world, people are much allured to scientific inventions and new discoveries. Science plays a vital role in the innovations of human life and their effective existence. As literature opens up a wide gate of inspiration and creativity it also connects the subject of science to explore the unexplored and experience the unseen. Herbert George Wells also known as H. G. Wells is best known for his science fiction novels and he is also called the father of science fiction. Some of his famous works are *The Time Machine* (1895), *The Island of Doctor Moreau* (1896), *The Invisible Man* (1897), *The War of the worlds* (1898) and *The War in the Air* (1907). As a socialist, he is famous for his social criticisms and his science fictions ultimately stood by the test of time.

In the present scenario, it is too hard to separate mankind from electronic gadgets and mobile phones have become the sixth finger in everyone's hand. Literature has already foreseen the future world and the merits and demerits that people will undergo with the advent of technology. Although it is a boon and blessing it is also dangerous and harmful, especially children are much addicted to the audio-visual attraction of the devices. H. G. Wells opens the eyes and minds of the readers in a whole new way he discusses alien invasions, airplanes, time machines and nuclear weapons in his fictions. He is a legendary author his science fictions are creative, social, political, realistic and sometimes pessimistic but always entertaining. His fictional visions of the future are widely celebrated as they predict, teach and reflect the real world.

His writings are enjoyed and lessons are gained by the generations as they always provide food for thought infinitely. As a pioneer in science fiction, his works manifest many futuristic predictions like television, phones, emails, audiobooks and airplanes in *Men Like Gods* (1923) and *When the Sleeper Wakes* (1899). He uses the technique of genetic engineering in the novel *The Island of Doctor Moreau* (1896) which deals with human-animal hybrid experiments. In *The War of the worlds* (1898) he introduces lasers and advanced energy weapons like microwaves, radio waves, sound waves and electromagnetic radiation which is six decades earlier than Theodore Maiman's first operational laser on 16th May 1960 at California's Hughes Research Laboratory. He uses the atomic bombs and nuclear proliferation in *The World Set Free* (1913) and explained the devastating power of the weapons that result in the worst death and destruction.

The Invisible Man (1897) is a tale about the life and death of a young scientist Griffin who goes mad due

to his curiousness. Having gained the knowledge of invisibility he makes himself invisible and uses his invention for nefarious purposes. The novel is a horror and also a fabulous classic that people of all ages enjoy all time. The themes of this novel include isolation, community and scientific advancement the novel also uses various figurative language and symbols. It is a science fiction with a deep message that has a well-known effect. The message is loud and clear that the medical discovery must be done within social and moral boundaries because failure in doing so might also carry unfavourable effects. This novel could be very particular because it deals with the existence of a scientist who invents a manner to change an object's reflective index to that of air. He invents it because it neither absorbs light nor displays it and consequently will become invisible. For the sake of clarity, he first experiments it on timber, then on a cat and after that he experiments it on himself and goes invisible. However, he does not know how to reverse the technique. It is an adventurous, fascinating and incredible novel that has kept its readers connected throughout. There is not any doubt that this novel is a giant hit with each of the readers and critics.

Griffin a weird and tragic character turns invisible by performing research. He becomes a scientist who labours recklessly day and night, is fed on drugs and becomes invisible. Initially, he was a student of medicine but then he switched to physics due to his enchantment in the direction of light and laws of mirrored image and refraction. However, his involvement with physics makes him even more interested in the invisibility and visibility of things. He is a secretive guy and accordingly, he hides the facts from anybody. He even did not inform his professor Oliver who could not get a touch of his experiment. The secrecy led Griffin to write his whole principle in Cipher Language so that no person could recognise it. He carried on his vivisection secretly as he knows that the law towards vivisection becomes very intense. He additionally gives strict instructions to Mrs. Hall that no one must be allowed inside his room. When Griffin achieves his experiment, he becomes pompous and conceited and dares to do something he would like. He thinks he has all of the power due to the fact nobody can harm him. However, it too made him helpless because he could not enjoy his fulfillment.

His selfishness has become a pest to him. People did not see his invisibility as an achievement they did not supply him with food, clothes to put on or a place to live. Everyone thought that he became an evil guy and this made him angry, sooner or later he stooped too low to end up as a thief. His father has passed away due to the fact that he has become a robber and also by making use of his invisibility, he has robbed many shops. This addiction to stealing no longer departs him until he dies. He desires to gather a huge sum of money as much as he can with the help of his invisibility. He had set a house on fire, robbed the dress of the house proprietor and exploited his invisibility to take advantage of Marvel as if he turned into his slave. He had emerged as unscrupulous too.

He becomes evil-minded because while his pal Kemp stood against him, he is even prepared to kill him. He forgot that it was Kemp who had given him food and refuge while he had no other helper. Kemp becomes a kind-hearted person who constantly desired to help his friend he tried his level best to turn Griffin towards humanity but failed. Society wants humans like him who can combat these anti-social people and can solve them properly. In terms of internal and external conflicts, Griffin is both the hero and the villain. He wanted to be a hero but ended up as his own enemy because of his greediness. People of the town come to know him when his invisibility is slowly uncovered. His zeal to be a greater person led him to his downfall. People started being afraid of him they wanted to discover and imprison him. Griffin simply runs from place to place seeking to live on by more and more debauched methods. So, his character also can be viewed as a scientist with perverted thoughts who has tried to damage humanity but ended up harming himself. Society never weeps for the person that harms it. Griffin is likewise taken as such someone and as a result society sooner or later made him pay his due. It is society itself that made him a horror due to the fact he was no longer rightly understood by society.

The crucial importance of literature in the field of science has increased in recent times. Though technology saves one's time and energy it should also be handled wisely as machines are mere programmed devices they do not have their own rational senses and only humans have to face the consequences. It is important that mankind has to rule the machines rather than machines ruling mankind, technology is for the people and by the people and people should not become slaves and servants of technology. Like drug addiction in the present times, everyone are addicted to advanced automation it makes them lazy and takes them away from the real world, family, friends and colleagues through its power of mesmerisation. As the world is now within each and everyone's hands, it's time to be more alert and cautious than before. Parents have more responsibility when compared to others that they must be attentive and vigilant toward their children because their innocence, curiosity and gullible nature should not be misused or misled by technology. Science says that children attain 90% of their brain development before the age of five and only 10% of brain development happens later. Teachers and parents must pay much attention to children below the age of five. They should always have an eye on children and must

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observe and watch their thoughts and activities this is possible only when they take the role of a friend in their lives.

It is also time to teach the older generation, senior citizens and grandparents about the operations of the technological devices that many fear, hesitate to learn, some are curious and the majority have an inferiority complex when youngsters use androids and other gadgets. Children and youngsters should take initiative measures to teach the grandparents, other rural and old age people about the uses, benefits, advantages and usage of these new arrivals. Love conquers all and people should have the humanity to do this. The past generation taught a lot to the present generation they are the storehouse of wisdom and experiences and now it is the turn of youngsters and children to give hope and knowledge to the older ones by comforting and holding their hands. When the wisdom of the old, the strength and intelligence of the youth and the heart of the child merge together the world will see a new magical earth. It will create an unimaginable powerful future for sure.

Time is precious because wasted time never returns awareness has to be brought regarding time management which will help people in work-life balance. There are also so many health issues arising in recent times due to more, continuous and longtime use of electronic devices and gadgets some lose their eyesight, face hearing impairments, hair fall, back pain, obesity, etc. Government has to take appropriate steps and measures in teaching awareness to the citizens and it is also the responsibility of each and every individual to promote a humanity-filled scientific society.

References

- [1] Wells, Herbert George. *The Invisible Man*. United Kingdom: C. Arthur Pearson P, Rupa. Co. Gopsons Papers Ltd. 1897.
- [2] Heinlein, Robert. *Philosophical and Military science fiction*. United States: MC Farland & Co Inc, December 1959.
- [3] Serling, Rod. *Fiction for all time*. England: Create Space Independent Publishing Platform, January 18, 2014. Print. Bio. A & E Television Network, 2015. Web. 21 Mar. 2015.
- [4] Burroughs, Edgar Rice. *Under the Moons of Mars*. United States: A.C. McClurg P, Barsoom series. 1917.

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SCHOOL HEALTH PROGRAMME: A STRATEGIC APPROACH FOR IMPROVING HEALTH & EDUCATION

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Introduction

Development of children and quality of their learning depends on a number of factors, including their own health status. Health promoting behaviour inculcated by the school not only contributes in physical development and health care of students, its spin-off improves awareness about health issues among the parents and local community as well. Strong relationship between health of students and their learning had inspired planners and educators to hundred years ago in developed countries to launch health related interventions in schools. Gradually, developing countries are also realizing importance of school health programme for quality education and overall health of the society, and are introducing its various components in their education systems.

Rationale and Significance

In our country, more than quarter of the population is in the age group 5 to 14 years, conventionally termed as the "school age group". This group, by itself, represents a tremendous human resource, a group whose health must be looked after, so that they develop into strong and prosperous citizens of tomorrow. This group also provides a unique opportunity to reach the young children and mould their behaviour in the desired way. School age children are more enthusiastic to be assigned new responsibilities, in addition they would act as agents for spreading the health awareness to their family members, thus facilitating the task of promoting primary health care. Health, nutrition and education are the pillars on which socio-economic development of nation rests. The need to have efficient school health services for supporting the general school education was amply recognised by the Govt of India. In 1960, the school health committee was set up under the chairmanship of Smt. Renuka Ray. The committee recommended that school health services should be a part and parcel of general health services. The functions of these services should be promotive, preventive and curative with special emphasis on medical examinations and health education of school children. The committee also recommended that health education should be included as a part of the general education in primary, middle and secondary schools and that the states should take immediate steps to publish text books on health education and to have health lessons included in other appropriate text books. Later, a seminar on school health services reiterated these recommendations. An intensive school health education project was launched in 1989 by the Central Health Education Bureau to help in improving the health and nutritional awareness of school children in rural areas. Despite the agreement on its importance as reflected by a number of committees, seminars and projects on school health, the actual progress on ground implementation has been rather slow. The general health care system overburdened with the care of patients, implementation of vertical and horizontal preventive programmes and administrative load seems to be left with little time and energy to address the issue of health examination, treatment and referral of school children. Similarly, much remains to be done as regards development and introduction of a formal health education curriculum in the schools. Hardly any targets seem to have been developed for monitoring the school health services. Interestingly, in 1981 the Govt of India constituted a high powered working group on Health for All by 2000 A.D. Recently School Health and Wellness Programme launched in February 2020 is being implemented in Govt. and Govt aided schools in districts under Ayushman Bharat. This School Health Programme is a joint initiative of ministry of Health & Family welfare and ministry of HRD, Govt of India.

Concept of School Health Programme

School Health Programme (SHP) addresses the health needs of children, both physical and mental and in addition it provides for long lasting healthy behaviours and habits which last forever. Schools are considered as place for learning where children learn not only subjective knowledge but also lifestyle practices and health seeking behaviour. SHP is one of the important components of total health care delivery system which helps to promote and maintain community wellbeing. School health refers to a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity among pupils, teachers and other school personnel. While School Health Service or Programme refers to need based comprehensive service rendered to

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pupils, teachers and other personnel in the school to promote, protect their health, prevent and control disease and maintain their health (K.K Gulani). A comprehensive SHP is an organised set of policies, procedures and activities designed to protect and promote the health and wellbeing of students and staff which has traditionally included health services, healthful school environment and health education.

Objectives

- 1) To provide age appropriate information about health and nutrition to the children in schools.
- 2) To promote healthy behaviours among the children that they will inculcate for life.
- 3) To detect and treat diseases early in children and adolescents including identification of malnourished and anaemic children with appropriate referrals to PHCs and hospitals.
- 4) To promote use of safe drinking water in schools
- 5) To promote safe menstrual hygiene practices by girls
- 6) To promote yoga and meditation through Health & Wellness Ambassadors.
- 7) To encourage research on health, wellness and nutrition for children.

School Health Promotion Activities

The health promotion activities will be given a special focus. Age appropriate health education for the students will be taken up to influence behaviour and enhance skills. The framework developed pays special attention to physical, psycho-social and mental aspects based on the developmental stages of the child. The broad components are:

Primary School

- 1) Health, growth and development
- 2) Personal safety
- 3) Nutrition and physical activity
- 4) Hygiene practices
- 5) Prevention of Diseases like

Middle School

- 1) Puberty and related changes
- 2) Eye care, oral hygiene
- 3) Nutrition
- 4) Bullying prevention
- 5) Meditation and Yoga
- 6) Internet safety and media literacy
- 7) Prevention of substance abuse
- 8) HIV/AIDS
- 9) Mental Health

High School

- 1) Prevention of substance abuse
- 2) Sexual & Reproductive Health
- 3) Violence Prevention
- 4) Unintentional Injury
- 5) Road safety
- 6) Nutrition
- 7) Meditation and Yoga

Health Screening

Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyakram (RBSK) is an important initiative aiming at early identification and early intervention for children from birth to 18 years to cover 4 'D's viz. Defects at birth, Deficiencies, Diseases, Development delays including disability. The 0-6 years' age group will be specifically managed at District Early Intervention Center (DEIC) level while for 6-18 years' age group, management of conditions will be done through existing public health facilities. DEIC will act as referral linkage for both the age groups. Once the child is screened and referred from school, it would be ensured that the necessary treatment/intervention is delivered at

zero cost to the family. The main objectives of these activities is to identify incipient diseases, disorders and disability by adequate timely action and to become the anchor promotive and preventive health.

Conclusion

Improving the health conditions and process of learning among school children through school based health and nutrition programmes is not a new concept. At present, most of the developed countries have institutionalized school health programmes as an integral part of their education systems. A number of national and international agencies have decades of experience in this area. School Health Programmes are primarily based on two pertinent premises. Firstly, the relationship of quality of learning with the health conditions of students, and secondly, responsibility of the state to facilitate smooth physical and mental growth of children for their future role as productive members of the society. A third dimension emphasized in certain situations is the potential contribution of students in dissemination of health and hygiene education messages to their parents and community at large. This phenomenon is also termed as child to child, and child to community transmission of information relating to health care and disease control. Global experiences link success in school health programme with partnership between various departments and agencies, including Education, Health, and Environment. Partnership and networking between relevant departments and agencies provide an opportunity for concerted action to broaden the scope of school health programmes and make them more effective and beneficial for the target groups. Effective school health programmes will transform schools into child-friendly environment, and contribute significantly to the promotion of Education for All.

Refernces

- [1] Shanna A. Sood M. Approach and strategies of child development in India: A Review. National Institute of Public Cooperation and Child Development, New Delhi, 1989 : 30-49.
- [2] Govt of India, Ministry of Human Resources Development, Department of Education. Selected Educational Indices : 1982-88; New Delhi, 1989.
- [3] Government of India, Ministry of Health. Report of the School Health committee (Part I). New Delhi, 1961: 1-93.
- [4] Central Health Education Bureau, Report on seminar on school health services. New Delhi, 1965: 1-71.

TEACHING COMPETENCIES OF A TEACHER IN THE CONTEXT OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The present study examines the competencies of a teacher in relation to multicultural education. For the future of educational system as well as the overall growth of nation is crucial to have a multicultural curriculum, multicultural learning teaching methods, equality in the classroom, a democratic school environment, equal access to opportunities, and the development of intercultural tolerance. An analysis of the literature reveals that the competencies of a teacher refer to an appropriate method of teaching students' specific knowledge, skills, and applications. For teachers to improve student performance, there are many different competencies they can acquire, including pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competencies. Similarly, as compared to teacher competencies, multicultural education plays a vital role in day-to-day life. The results of the study reveal that multicultural education will enable students to assimilate into a global culture in today's competitive 21st century. Multicultural education is a modern strategy for reforming education that explores and solves all of its current issues, breakdowns, and discriminatory practices. Every teacher should be multicultural and have a good teaching competencies the 21st century, and then our education system will reach a higher standard.

Keywords: *Education, Multicultural Education, Teacher, Teaching Competencies.*

Background of the Study

Education needs to be more inclusive, and all students should have access to it regardless of their social status. The goal of a 21st-century education is to equip students with the skills necessary to be thoughtful, engaged citizens of their communities, countries, and global community. Education for ethics, values, honesty, integrity, and transparency is implemented into school curricula. Education is a powerful weapon to change the world in a better way, and it is very essential for the welfare of societies in all aspects. "Culture is an attitude of mind, an inclination of the spirit, and those who yearn for it wish to have a vision of greatness; they sit in the presence of nobility and see the highest reach and scope of the spirit of man." According to the University Education Commission, 1948-1949 Culture is a dynamic social reality. It is never static. The cultural configurations of a society or group are ever-changing. The present cultural dimension is constantly growing to include new points of view. Culture is created through the transmission of beliefs, practices, knowledge, attitudes, customs, and values from one generation to the next. Indians are proud to claim that their nation is one of the world's most diverse. Multiculturalism is cultural diversity. Any culture's future is determined by the ideology of the educated class in that nation, which implies that the education system in that nation has an impact on that culture. The process of classifying all religions and individuals from various cultures equally and without making any distinctions based on race or culture is known as multiculturalism. The wealth of the nation is its knowledgeable and equitable community. Any nation's development is based on the progression of its society. Multiculturalism promotes principles of inclusion, democracy, and a sense of togetherness, among many other positive traits. To fully understand the concept of secularism, multicultural education is crucial for instilling in students the belief that we are all Indians with no cultural differences. Teacher should trained the youth for better citizens and develops the democratic values of equality, liberty, fraternity, and cooperative living. It also enables the youth to develop the spirit of love, tolerance, cooperation, equality, and empathy towards other citizens and helps us understand their problems better.

Review of Related Literature

Jagannath (2004). The main objective of the study is to "assist all students in developing the knowledge, attitudes, and abilities necessary to function successfully in a pluralistic democratic society". Students are taught how to interact with people from diverse groups in order to create a civic and moral community that works for the common good. Banks (2006). Education in multiculturalism prepares students for success in a pluralistic, democratic society. Since it connects knowledge, values, empowerment, and action, multicultural education sees citizen participation as a crucial component of education. The main objective of multicultural education is to

restructure schools so that all students will learn how to function in a society that is racially and ethnically diverse. Maria (2007) conducted research that provides a framework for analyzing how levels of conceptual change and cultural competency are progressed through in teacher education programs. This study revealed that in teacher education methods courses, a focus on diversity is introduced through exposure to and examination of multicultural theories and practices, use of situated learning pedagogies in local school and community contexts, and chances for self- reflection and the examination of preconceived notions about oneself and others. As they seek their master's degrees, teachers have more chances to consider and analyze sociocultural diversity. Also, elements of the second and third levels of understanding getting specific and taking action might be covered in teacher training programmes. Thakur and Monika (2014). This study uses descriptive research to assess teacher competencies and professional qualities. In the study, various teacher competencies were defined. The study's primary goals were to identify the elements of teacher competencies and the variations in student perceptions of the teaching abilities of various teachers. In view of the data analysis, the researcher came towards the conclusions that were presented in the results. The majority of students support teachers' personal, social, and professional competencies to boost students' performance. Yasir .et.al (2019). A descriptive qualitative study was conducted on teacher competencies. Findings of this study demonstrate that teachers continue to play an important role in the classroom. The use of different teaching methods and strategies depends on the characteristics of the students in each type of school. The role of teachers in multicultural classrooms, strategies, and media.

Research Question

1. What are the competencies of a teacher in relation to multicultural education?

Competencies of a Teacher in Relation to Multicultural Education

Teachers should act as living examples or ideals that their students can look up to for objectivity, attitude, and impartial activity. This is vital when society is threatened by narrow bigotry, religious fanaticism, and irrational superstition. Students can acquire the knowledge and commitments needed to make reflective decisions and to take personal, social, and civic action to promote democracy and democratic living. Helps foster a scientific spirit. It releases the individual from the bonds of blind faith. Secular education promotes the scientific values of rationality, objectivity, and open-mindedness. Children should get an education that will enhance their character and moral behavior, irrespective of their religion. It enables us to understand the point of view of people who are different from us. It trains the youth to be better citizens and develops the democratic values of equality, liberty, fraternity, and cooperative living. It also enables the youth to develop the spirit of love, tolerance, cooperation, equality, and empathy towards other citizens and helps us understand their problems better. Teachers know when and how to use current educational technology, as well as the most appropriate type and level of technology to maximize student learning. At the base level, the teacher is the most vital factor in implementing all educational reforms at the base level. All content knowledge learning should incorporate and expand upon the knowledge and experience that students bring to the classroom. Some of them are as under;

- 1)To gain knowledge of how to assess information from various perspectives.
- 2)To form a global, national, and ethnic identity.
- 3)To equip students with critical thinking and decision-making abilities. Teachers are the strongest source for promoting education in a healthy way to build the nation.
- 4)To be a good teacher, one must have good teaching competencies to get the best results in the profession of teaching.
- 5)The social student is the center of society, making the student-centered curriculum
- 6)vitaly important in multicultural education. Competencies simply mean the integration of the components of knowledge, expertise, viewpoints, usefulness, and incitation that are needed for success in any profession for an individual.
- 7)Described teaching competency as the activities and disciplines of teaching: becoming
- 8)proficient and evolving learning materials; designing and arranging lessons; and administering and assessing the learners' learning outcomes.

Competency refers to the appropriate method of teaching student's specific knowledge, skills, and applications. For teachers to improve student performance, there are many different competencies they can acquire, including pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competencies. It is the type of skill required to make teaching more effective and produce the best results. Similarly, as compared to teacher competencies, multicultural education plays a vital role in day-to-day life. Since education is a tool for cultivating, preserving, and transforming culture, it is crucial to impart multiculturalism in education in a nation like India that has

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influenced both multiculturalism and secularism. India is a country with many different religions, languages, educational systems, traditions, and values. Multicultural education will enable students to assimilate into a global culture in today's competitive 21st century. Multicultural education is a modern strategy for reforming education that explores and solves all of its current issues, breakdowns, and discriminatory practices. It is rooted in the ideals of social justice, educational equity, and a commitment to facilitating that all students receive educational experiences that allow them to realize their full potential as learners and as socially engaged, locally, nationally, and internationally active individuals. Multicultural education recognizes the importance of education in establishing the framework for social reform and the removal of oppression and injustice. Multicultural events encourage parents, teachers, and students to grow through their interactions with one another on a daily basis in a global setting. This is facilitated in a natural and secure setting by multicultural classrooms.

Methodology

In this context to identify the competencies of a teacher in relation to multicultural education. The researcher opted the secondary source of data and descriptive qualitative methods for the study.

Conclusion

Teachers play an important role in the classroom. Teachers should have to be multicultural and should also have teaching competency. As our society is dynamic in nature. Our society will become a welfare state where we respect the diversity (culture, class, religion and creed) of our country. The nation of India and the individual benefit from the promotion of Indian arts and culture. Result of the study shows that culture awareness and expression play a significant role in promoting both individual and societal well-being. Students can develop a positive sense of cultural identity and conscience by becoming knowledgeable about the history, traditions, arts, and languages of their own culture. Therefore, cultural awareness and expression play a significant role in promoting both individual and societal well-being. Conclusion of the study reveals that multicultural education would give students a thorough understanding of the political and economic systems of the world, foster critical thinking, foster empathy and respect for others, and advance cross-cultural awareness. Helping students, developing knowledge and commitments are necessary to make thoughtful decisions and to engage in personal, social, and civic action to advance democracy and democratic living is a key objective of multicultural education.

References

- [1] Banks (Eds.), Handbook of research on multicultural education, 2nd Edition (pp. 491-514). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- [2] 491-514). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- [3] Dunghaus, S.D. (2021). multiculturalism In Education. Educational Resurgence Journal, vol.3, p-p 46 - 48.
- [4] Jagannath, V. K. (2004). Dimensions of multicultural education. 244. https://openlibrary.org/works/OL10232505W/Dimensions_of_Multicultural_Education
- [5] Kuyini, A. B., Yeboah, K. A., Das, A. K., Alhassan, A. M., & Mangope, B. (2016). Ghanaian teachers: Competencies perceived as important for inclusive education. International Journal of Inclusive Education, 20, 1009-1023
- [6] Maria. (2007). Building Teacher Competency to Work with Diverse Learners in the Context of International Education. Teacher Education Quarterly, vol.34, p.p -75-94.
- [7] <https://in.docs.wps.com/l/sIB2j-NW8Aaq-wJ4G?sa=03&st=0t>
- [8] <https://in.docs.wps.com/l/sIPuj-NW8AbzHwJ4G?sa=03&st=0t>
- [9] <https://www.accreditedschoolsonline.org/resources/student-diversity-multicultural/>
- [10] <https://web.uri.edu/teach/multicultural/>
- [11] <https://idronline.org/nep-2020>

CHALLENGES AND SOCIAL INCLUSION OF ORPHAN CHILDREN

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Abstract

Childhood is considered as an important phase of life. In this stage, parents play a climacteric role. It is the responsibility of parents to fulfil both physiological and psychological needs of the child, to provide him good education and guide him for the challenges of life. Every child who passes through this censorious stage of life without enjoying the attention and care of parents is called an orphan. According to United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), India has 29.6 million orphaned and abandoned children since 2018. Only a fraction of these children is ending with a family due to low adoption rates in India. The objective of this paper is to study the challenges faced by orphan students and to study the legislative provisions for the orphans. In this study the researcher will also try to suggest measures for the education of orphans. To know the challenges and legislative provisions, the researcher has used analytical research method under qualitative types for the study. The study also focuses on the education of orphan. As Education can strengthen significant improvements in the lives of orphans and vulnerable children.

Keywords: *Orphans, Challenges, Issues, Legislative Provisions, Education*

Introduction

Education is a systematic process through which a child or an adult acquires knowledge, experience and sound attitude. It makes an individual civilized, refined, cultured and educated. For a civilized and socialized society, education is the only means to progress. When India achieved its independence, the literacy rate was only 12%. Afterwards India made massive progress in the economic and social sphere. The literacy rate increased to 74.04% in the year 2011. Although it looks like a huge achievement, but still there are many people in India who are deprived of education. Childhood is considered as an important phase of life. In this stage, parents play a climacteric role. It is the responsibility of parents to fulfil both physiological and psychological needs of the child, to provide him good education and guide him for the challenges of life. Every child who passes through this censorious stage of life without enjoying the attention and care of parents is called an orphan. As we can see that the graph of education is increasing, but still there are lot of children particularly orphan, destitute and poor children who are not able to receive education. According to the United Nations 2.63 million children and young people worldwide cannot attend school or receive education, 53% of the 61 million children of primary school age 6 to 11 years who cannot attend school are girls. (Nar,2020).

Orphan Children in India

India is the world's largest democracy with a population of over a billion people, of which 400 million are children. According to United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), India has 29.6 million orphaned and abandoned children since 2018. This is more than the population of Sri Lanka. Only a fraction of these children is ending with a family due to low adoption rates in India.

Objectives

- 1) To study the challenges faced by orphan students
- 2) To study the legislative provisions for the orphans
- 3) To suggest measures for the education of orphans

Methodology

To know the challenges, legislative provisions and nep recommendations, the researcher has used analytical research method under qualitative types for the study

Issues and Challenges

In India, a large number of orphanages run on charities and thus, have an unstable income. Orphanages can be turned into a hub of criminal activities, such as human trafficking, rape, cruelty against children, the intoxication of children, child prostitution, child pornography, forced into begging, etc. Durualt and Cicekoglu (2013) conducted a study on "A study on the loneliness levels of adolescents who live in an orphan age those who live with their families." . It was concluded that adolescents living in an orphan age experienced higher level of

loneliness than those living with their families, and the differences was statistically significant. There have been cases of human trafficking and forced labour in the past as well. Children, especially orphans separated from their parents or with no parents, are exploited on a large basis. **Wangler (2019)** conducted a study on “Child care institutions in Manipur: services and facilities”. It was conducted to identify the various services and facilities available for children in child care institutions as laid in the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act, 2015. The findings of the study revealed that the services and facilities were unsatisfactory, there was improper functioning of non-institutional care, there was absence of professional staff, negligence in meeting the special needs of children and less importance was given to children’s rehabilitation and social integration. **Bhat (2014)** conducted a study on “A study of emotional stability and depression in orphan secondary school students. The study revealed that there was a significant difference in emotional stability and depressive levels between the two age groups. Orphans were found at the lower side of emotional stability and higher level of depression as compared to their counterpart non-orphan secondary school students.

Challenges Faced by Children Orphans

The low number of Child Care Institutions: According to a study, only 0.5% of orphaned children reach orphanages. One in five districts in the country does not have even a single orphanage home. This results in numerous children reach the road and commit petty crimes for their survival. The mandate of Child Protection Services or CPS under the Government of India was to protect these vulnerable children. However, the coverage of this program has been less than 1 lakh children per year. The study by the Ministry of Women and Child Development (MWCD) undertaken in 2016-17 has revealed that there are 9589 CCIs/Homes (registered/unregistered); 91 per cent of which are run by non-government organizations, and only 9 per cent are government supported. One in five districts in the country does not have even a single orphanage. A majority of districts does not have the minimum three orphanages needed (one for children of less than 6 years of age and one each for boys and girls of 6-18 years respectively). The government’s annual expenditure on child protection (covering the entire gamut of child rights) is Rs 1500 crores : it amounts to less than Rs 2 per child per day, covering food, clothing, education and medical needs for the 30 million abandoned children! **No separate legislation:** In India, Orphans and vulnerable children do not have separate legislation. Instead, they are part of the Juvenile Justice Act. But the primary focus of the Act is to provide punishments to children under 18 Years. **Low adoption rates:** Ironically millions of children without parents and there is a rise in the number of infertile couples. But still, the adoption rate is not improved in India. According to the Central Adoption Resource Authority’s (CARA) adoption statistics, there were only 3,276 in-country adoptions in 2017-2018. This is a dismal figure when compared to the number of orphaned children in India.

Central Adoption Resource Authority

Central Adoption Resource Authority (CARA) is a statutory body of Ministry of Women & Child Development, Government of India.

Adoption statistics

Year	In country adoption	Inter country
2010	5693	628
2011	5964	629
2012-2013	4694	308
2013-2014	3924	430
2014-2015	3988	374
2015-2016	3011	666
2016-2017	3210	578
2017-2018	3376	651
2018-2019	3351	653
2019-2020	3142	394
2021-2022	2991	414

No separate legislation: In India, Orphans and vulnerable children do not have separate legislation. Instead, they are part of the Juvenile Justice Act. But the primary focus of the Act is to provide punishments to children under 18 Years.

Legislative provisions

The Orphanages and Other Charitable Homes (Supervision and Control) Act, 1960. The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015, doesn't necessarily limit itself to orphans but is a law relating to children. In accordance with laws related to orphanages, this law encompasses aspects such as little kids, in need of care, protection, and nurturing, and caters towards their development, education, treatment, rehabilitation, etc. The POCSO Act of 2012 has been of aid several times in past cases of sexual crimes committed against orphans. It is an Act that includes and recognizes sexual assault against children in general. Rights of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, deals with the education of children. Established institutions, funded by charity or the government, for the upkeep of the children in their organization, can siphon out the funds for their personal use and not provide the compulsory education needed for the betterment of such children. This Act submits directions and grievances in cases like these. The Board of Control can also cancel the certificate of authentication and permission to run an Orphanage, upon trial. The Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986, puts a prohibition on employment of children, below the age of 15 years, in any sort of labour, and also bans several occupations to children who haven't yet crossed 18 years of age. This Act prohibits the Orphanages from sending children to work as laborers or selling them as slaves. The Information and Technology Act of 2000, codifies the provisions against child pornography. Anyone who produces distributes, or causes to be published or transmitted any digital content portraying minors engaging in explicit sexual acts or behaviour, would be held as a criminal by law and would face serious consequences.

Suggestions for the Education of Orphans

Education can strengthen significant improvements in the lives of orphans and vulnerable children. On top of instilling life skills and knowledge, it can also contribute greatly to a child's psychosocial development and provide a safe, structured environment during an immensely important period of their lives. By opening the door to quality education, we are able to unlock the potential of these children and a better future for them. Education is the difference between poverty and plenty. By educating as many orphans in the world, we can gradually solve the world's orphan crisis.

Teachers should also play their roles to encourage the orphaned students to learn and provide necessary academic support when appropriate. Orphaned students need love and care in order to make them eager to learn. Orphaned students should be involved in class activities, sports, and games thus they may not feel isolated from the society. Their self-esteem will be raised through achievement of some tasks. The ministry of education and their stakeholders should plan and establish regular seminars to enable teachers to be equipped with skills and tactics to deal with the challenges facing orphaned students in academic performance. Also necessary support in teaching and learning materials should be provided to enhance the academic performance of orphaned students. NGOs are also playing a leading role in taking care of orphan and abandoned children. Since the government of India funds only 9% of child care Institutions, it is our duty to support all NGO orphanages with donations and advocacy

References

- [1] Bhat, N.M. (2014). A study of emotional stability and depression in orphan secondary school students. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research*, 3(2), 95-100. Retrieved from http://ijep.r.org/doc/V3_Is2_June14/ij20.pdf on 21 November, 202
- [2] Dutta, N. (2018) Street children in India: A study on their access to health and education. *International Journal of Child, Youth and Family Studies*, 9(1), 69-82. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18357/ijcyfs91201818120> on 20 October, 2020.
- [3] Gupta, S. (2010). *Education in emerging India*. Delhi: Shipra Publications
- [4] Nar, C. (2020). Orphan Report, Research, INSAMER, IHH Humanitarian Relief Foundation. Retrieved from https://insamer.com/en/2020-orphan-report_2928.html on 7 June, 2020
- [5] Singaravelu, G. (2018). *Education in contemporary India*. New Delhi: Neel Kamal Publications Pvt. Ltd.
- [6] Orphanage Laws in India: Protection of Orphan Children - Black n' White Journal (bnwjjournal.com)
- [7] Orphans : The Forgotten Children of India (serudsindia.org)
- [8] https://insamer.com/en/2020-orphan-report_2928.htm

ASSESSMENT FOR LEARNING AND TEACHING HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

This article addresses the issue of assessment for learning and teaching higher education and remedies through learning systems. In our schools many hours are spent teaching how to write and read in English and other subjects. But hardly any hour is spent in teaching how to speak it. Thus teaching of communication is curriculum, particularly in the selection of material, which goes into the communication textbooks. Only then will the teachers be able to perform their tasks in the classroom meaningfully. So it is high time we changed our mindset and began to relook at the learning methods of communication from the very elementary stage and take corrective steps at higher institution level, particularly teaching the speaking skills.

Introduction

Communication is learning and teaching is considered an international language in English. The communication language has been used in India ever since the days of the east India Company. The problems of teaching and learning English have, however, continued to further challenge. Teaching and learners in them became a ruling language and then also there was no problem. When it was dressed up in the perhaps our future generations will also face the problem.

Curriculum is a Communication Skill

The major thrust is the revised curriculum is on communication skill which is the basis for all learning and the development of their skill is now brought to the realm of all teachers and all classes and not restricted to language classes alone. There has been a conscious effort to reduce the learning load of the students, without lowering the competitiveness of the systems as the parents' attitude and aspiration need to be respected. For an effective curriculum transaction, a set of strategies is recommended for adoption to help the matriculation system to achieve the mission of providing effective and competitive education.

Teacher Orientation Programmes

General training programmes to all teachers other than language to train in the communication skill along with their expertise in their specialized subject areas. Introduction of the common examination system at the end of each stage of matriculation school system to ensure quality and comparability of standards among schools in the state. Establishing "a state level quality assurance" to replace the existing the type of quality control without any extra financial commitment. Preparation of teachers handbook or manual

Designing Materials

The systematic steps that designers of instructional materials follow in the production of materials are:

- 1) Selection of the language input that would best realize the syllabus, that is, the language objectives and content that have been pre-specified or prescribed beforehand.
- 2) Organization of all these into learning units or lessons suitable for a classroom.
- 3) Grading and arranging all these in the most appropriate manner from simple to difficult with a view to promoting learning in the most efficient and effective manner possible.

So, the teachers need the support of the materials to carry on day to day teaching and teach their learners a language. They also need the direction that instructional methods provide.

Findings

The rural learners are unable to speak English fluently because the teachers themselves speak in the regional language. The rural students do not have proficiency due to their inhibitions. Most of the time rural learners think only in the regional language, and tend to make mistakes in subject verb agreement. Vocabulary building must be encouraged among the rural learners. The language games should be made more interesting to the rural students because they enjoyed language games. The usage of dictionary should be encouraged.

Training

Almost all members of the panel except the learner expressed that lack of periodical training and in-service programmes for communication teachers was a challenge.

Infrastructures

Teachers enunciated that the infrastructure facilities provided by certain management did not encourage the practitioners to provide students through practice using innovative methods.

Some Comments on Teachers

- 1) Except few lectures and teachers, overall fascinating.....
- 2) Teachers are cooperative.
- 3) Good interaction among teachers and students.
- 4) Presentations by Were bench markers....
- 5) I like thee politeness of all faculty members except.....

Conclusion

Learner's active learning is vitally important for the mastery of skills, such as communication skills, critical thinking and problem solving. Active learning relies on fostering learner's classroom engagement and this can be done effectively through pair or group activities. The valuable learning experience to learners and gives them the opportunity to experience practically the ideas presented.

References

- [1] The journal – LVI/5,2014
- [2] Self supporting....curriculum. Dr.C.Swathanthira Kumar.
- [3] Teaching in India – S.Kudchedkar.

NEURAL BASES OF EMOTIONAL REGULATION : A BRIEF REVIEW

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Abstract

This paper reviews insights from research studies that explore neural bases of emotional regulation. Emotion refers to a type of mental state that occurs almost all times in human life. Emotion regulation is a sequence of versatile emotional circumstances within a social event (Gross & Barrett, 2011). Regions of the human brain such as the orbital frontal cortex, anterior cingulate cortex, amygdala, and other associated regions form complex circuits which involve the regulation of emotion. Structure and function of this circuit influence by both inheritable and environmental factors. Effective emotion regulation is crucial for psychosocial well-being. (Berking & Wupperman, 2012). Defective emotion regulation leads to impulsive aggression and violence. (Davidson et al., 2000).

Keywords: *Emotion Regulation, Reappraisal, Neural Circuits, Amygdala, Pre-Frontal*

Introduction

Emotions are responses to situations that are seen as personally relevant and represent the vital driving force of human behavior (Ekman, 1992). Emotions are expressed at three distinct levels such as subjective experience (how an individual 'feels' them); expressive behavior (how an individual acts them out); physiology (the bodily changes that accompany emotions, such as increased heart rate and blood pressure, and hormonal changes). Neuroscientific research studies revealed that both psychological and neurobiological mechanisms are involved in effective emotion regulation. (Gross, 1998; Ochsner & Gross, 2007). Prefrontal structures regulate limbic regions which leads to effective cognitive control strategies. At the neural activity level, both the amygdala and medial prefrontal cortex were involved in both strategies of mindfulness and cognitive reappraisal.

Neural Bases of Emotion Regulation: A Brief Review

Emotions are the main building blocks of memorable experiences (Bastiaansen, et al., 2019). Developmental research studies revealed that the emotion regulation ability improves with age. Emotion regulation ability is related to the functions of prefrontal brain regions which are involved in cognitive control and executive functioning that improves late in development. (Martin & Ochsner, 2016). The prime function of emotion regulation is to increase emotional arousal or positive valence to enhance learning, and it aids to decrease emotional responses that might be blocking the successful encoding of novel information. Gender differences in emotion regulation based on the centromedian amygdala indicate that men and women may differ in the neural circuits associated with emotion representation and integration. (Wu et al., 2016).

Basic emotion theory revealed that every basic emotion has a particular brain locus. Distinct emotions have different physiological signatures. (Gu et al., 2015). Reappraisal is found to be effective at decreasing or increasing responses in systems related to emotional responding. Amygdala is a subcortical structure vital for signaling the presence, and modulating the encoding, of emotion-related stimuli (Phelps & LeDoux, 2005). The core site of all negative emotions (fear and anger) is identified as the amygdala. (Gu et al., 2019). Affective responses of the individual are represented by a cortical region insula. (Uddin et al., 2014). Neuromodulators such as dopamine (DA), norepinephrine (NE), serotonin (5-HT) and acetylcholine (Ach) are prime neural bases of primary emotions namely joy, fear, missing and sadness. (Gu et al., 2015).

Synthesis and Conclusion

This review summarized few neurological bases of emotion regulation. Regulating one's emotion is a pivotal skill in day today life. Emotion regulation is associated with physical, mental, and emotional well-being. Emotion regulation ability improves with age and it depends on the function of prefrontal brain regions.

References

- [1] Bastiaansen, M., Lub, X. D., Mitas, O., Jung, T. H., Ascenção, M. P., Han, D. I., ... & Strijbosch, W. (2019). Emotions as core building blocks of an experience. *International Journal of Contemporary*

Hospitality Management.

- [2] Berking, M., & Wupperman, P. (2012). Emotion regulation and mental health: recent findings, current challenges, and future directions. *Current opinion in psychiatry*, 25(2), 128-134.
- [3] Davidson, R. J., Putnam, K. M., & Larson, C. L. (2000). Dysfunction in the neural circuitry of emotion regulation--a possible prelude to violence. *science*, 289(5479), 591-594.
- [4] Ekman, P. (1992), "An argument for basic emotions", *Cognition and Emotion*, Vol. 6, No. 3-4, pp. 169-200.
- [5] Gross, J. J., & Feldman Barrett, L. (2011). Emotion generation and emotion regulation: One or two depends on your point of view. *Emotion review*, 3(1), 8-6. doi: 10.1177/1754073910380974.
- [6] Gross, J. J. (1998). The emerging field of emotion regulation: An integrative review. *Review of general psychology*, 2(3), 271-299. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.2.3.271>
- [7] Gu, S., Wang, F., Yuan, T., Guo, B., & Huang, J. H. (2015). Differentiation of primary emotions through neuromodulators: review of literature. *International Journal of Neurology Research*, 1(2), 43-50.
- [8] Gu, S., Wang, F., Yuan, T., Guo, B., & Huang, J. H. (2015). International Journal of Neurology Research. *Int. J. of Neurol. Res*, 2, 43-50.
- [9] Gu, S., Wang, F., Cao, C., Wu, E., Tang, Y. Y., & Huang, J. H. (2019). An integrative way for studying neural basis of basic emotions with fMRI. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 13, 628
- [10] Martin, R. E., & Ochsner, K. N. (2016). The Neuroscience of Emotion Regulation Development: Implications for Education. *Current opinion in behavioral sciences*, 10, 142-148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2016.06.006>
- [11] Ochsner, K. N., & Gross, J. J. (2007). The neural architecture of emotion regulation. *Handbook of emotion regulation*, 1(1), 87-109.
- [12] Phelps, E. A., & LeDoux, J. E. (2005). Contributions of the amygdala to emotion processing: from animal models to human behavior. *Neuron*, 48(2), 175-187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2005.09.025>
- [13] Uddin, L. Q., Kinnison, J., Pessoa, L., & Anderson, M. L. (2014). Beyond the tripartite cognition-emotion-interoception model of the human insular cortex. *Journal of cognitive neuroscience*, 26(1), 16-27.
- [14] Wu, Y., Li, H., Zhou, Y., Yu, J., Zhang, Y., Song, M., ... & Jiang, T. (2016). Sex-specific neural circuits of emotion regulation in the centromedial amygdala. *Scientific reports*, 6(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep23112>

INFLUENCE OF ACADEMIC BACKGROUND ON ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract

Healthcare professionals play a central and critical role in improving access and quality healthcare for the society. The healthcare providers such as pharmaceutical companies are appointing medical sales representatives to meet their customers, promote the products, and to convince them that their company products or services will satisfy their needs. But, in reality, the medical sales representatives are mostly a mixed category from science or arts or other subjects academic stream, studied in English or regional language, having work experience or no experience. The researcher made a descriptive study to identify the influence of academic background on achievement motivation of healthcare professionals working in TTK Healthcare Ltd. Among the total population of 1,100 healthcare professionals working in TTK Healthcare Ltd., the investigator selected a sample 592 by using simple random sampling technique. The results of the study show that the level of achievement motivation of the healthcare professionals working in TTK Healthcare Ltd., is at the moderate level. The result also shows that there is no significant difference among those healthcare professionals who have graduated in arts, science, and other subjects in their achievement motivation.

Keywords: *Healthcare Professionals, Academic Background, Achievement Motivation*

Introduction

The World Health Organization (2022) defines health as a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Healthcare is the improvement of health through the prevention, diagnosis, treatment, amelioration, or cure of disease. Healthcare is delivered by healthcare professionals and allied health fields. Healthcare professionals play a central and critical role in improving access and quality healthcare for the population. They provide essential services that promote health, prevent diseases and deliver healthcare services to individuals, families and communities based on the primary healthcare approach (World Health Organization, 2022). The category of healthcare professionals includes physicians, nurses, technicians, medical assistants, dentists, midwives, radiographers, pharmacists, physiotherapists, optometry, audiology, psychology, occupational therapy, physical therapy, athletic training, and other health professions. India has a mixed healthcare system, inclusive of public and private healthcare service providers (Sheikh, 2015).

Pharmaceutical Industry – An Overview

A pharmaceutical company or drug company, is a commercial business licensed to research, develop, market and/or distribute drugs to improve life expectancy of mankind or animal welfare. The pharmaceutical companies are appointing medical sales representatives to meet their customers, promote the products, and to convince them that their company products or services will satisfy their needs. medical sales representatives are expected to increase the company product demand by highlighting feature, advantage and benefits. Hence, generally, the pharmaceutical companies recruit medical sales representatives with a background of sales experience, sound knowledge in science, and good communication skills.

Need and Significance of the Study

Medical representatives, also known as ‘medical sales representatives’ or ‘professional sales representatives’ or ‘territory business managers’ sell and promote companies' medications, prescription drugs, and medical equipment (Betterteam, n.d.). Rajat Saha (2020) mentioned that medical sales representatives are expected to have core skills such as writing skills, reading skills, and oral communication (listening and speaking skills). As the medical sales representatives are being the part in providing good healthcare to the society, the researcher considered medical sales representatives as healthcare professionals. The researcher explored a descriptive study to identify the influence of academic qualification on achievement motivation of healthcare professionals who are working in TTK Healthcare Ltd., a pan India pharmaceutical company.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Achievement Motivation

Achievement refers to competence and quality of success. On the other hand, motivation refers to the energization and direction of behaviour. Thus, achievement motivation may be defined as the energization and direction of competence-relevant behaviour or why and how people strive toward competence (success) and away from incompetence (failure) (Baumeister & Vohs, 2007). The Encyclopaedia of Child Behaviour and Development defines achievement motivation as the need for excellence and significant accomplishment, despite what rewards may be offered after the achievement has been met (Hsieh, 2011).

Objective of the Study

To find out the level of achievement motivation of healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., with regard to academic background.

Hypothesis of the Study

There is no significant difference among the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts, science, and other subjects in their achievement motivation.

Methodology of the Study

The proposed study is a descriptive design with a focus on examining correlation among the chosen study variables. The investigator used survey research method to find out the influence of academic background on achievement motivation among healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd. The population for the present study includes all the 1,100 healthcare professionals working in TTK Healthcare Ltd. The investigator selected a sample of 592 healthcare professionals working in TTK Healthcare Ltd., by adopting simple random sampling technique and collected the data pertaining to the present study through email.

Tools Used in the Study

A tool in research is a data collecting device. Data collection is the process of collecting information needed to answer the research problem (Nalzar, 2012). Keeping the objective of the study in mind, the Achievement Motivation Scale constructed and validated by the Investigator (2021) was used apart from the Personal Data Form, designed by the Investigator.

Data Analysis and Findings of the Study

Objective

To find out the level of achievement motivation of healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., with regard to academic background.

Table 1 Level of Achievement Motivation of Healthcare Professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., with regard to Academic Background

Academic Background	Achievement Motivation					
	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Arts Graduates	67	22.2	180	59.6	55	18.2
Science Graduates	48	19.6	150	61.2	47	19.2
Other Subject Graduates	10	22.2	27	60.0	08	17.8

It is inferred from the Table 1 that 22.2% of healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts subjects have low, 59.6% of them have moderate, and 18.2% of them have high level of achievement motivation. Further, the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in other subjects 22.2% of them have low, 60.0% of them have moderate, and 17.8% of them have high level of achievement motivation. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Level of Achievement Motivation of Healthcare Professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., with regard to Academic Background

Hypothesis of the Study

There is no significant difference among the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts, science, and other subjects in their achievement motivation.

Table 2 Difference among the Healthcare Professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have Graduated in Arts, Science, and Other Subjects in their Achievement Motivation

Academic Background	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	Calculated 'F' Value	Remarks
Achievement Motivation	Between	1290.336	2, 589	645.168	0.216	NS
	Within	1763152.879		2993.468		

Note. At 5% level of significance for df (2, 589), the table value of 'F' is 2.995.

NS = Not Significant.

It is inferred from the Table 2 that the calculated 'F' value (0.216) is less than the table value (2.995) for df 2, 589 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted as the result shows that there is no significant difference among the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts, science and other subjects in their achievement motivation. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no significant difference among the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts, science and other subjects in their achievement motivation.

Conclusion

The results of the study show that the level of achievement motivation of majority of the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., is at the moderate level. The result also shows that there is no significant difference among the healthcare professionals in TTK Healthcare Ltd., who have graduated in arts, science and other subjects in their achievement motivation. But for the growth and sustenance of Pharma companies including the TTK Healthcare Ltd., in the midst of heavy competitions from different existing and emerging national, and international companies, need to have highly achievement motivated healthcare professionals.

References

- [1] Betterteam. (n.d.). Medical representative job description. <https://www.betterteam.com/medical-representative-job-description>
- [2] Nalzar, L. M. (2012, June 9). Chapter 9-Methods of Data Collection [Power Point Slides]. SlideShare. <https://www.slideshare.net/ludymae/chapter-9methods-of-data-collection>
- [3] Saha, R. (2020). You can be a medical representative, Chennai.

INVESTIGATING STUDY ON LOAD BALANCING

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Abstract

In cloud computing, a lot of challenging issues like the server failures, confidentiality mismatch, improper workloads, etc. are still was been allegations the efficiency of cloud systems in real-world scenarios. Because of this reason, many research works are being performed to overcome the shortcoming of existing systems. Among them, load balancing come off as the most critical issue that worsen the performance of the cloud sector, and hence there necessitates the optimal load balancing with optimal task scheduling. With the intention of accomplishing optimal load balancing by efficient task allotment, this paper plans to develop an advanced load balancing study on highlighting the various parameters.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Load Balancing, Virtualization

Introduction

What is cloud computing?

Cloud computing is a general term for anything that involves delivering hosted services over the internet. These services are categorized into three main categories or types of cloud computing: infrastructure as a service (*IaaS*), platform as a service (*PaaS*) and software as a service (*SaaS*) [1]. The definition of cloud computing provided by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) says that: "Cloud computing is a model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing Resources. Cloud Computing is a robust model that allows users and organizations to purchase required services according to their needs. The model offers many services such as storage, platforms for deployment, convenient access to web services, and so on [2]". So through this cloud computing there is no need to store the data on desktops, portables etc. we can store the data on servers and you can access data through internet. Cloud computing provides better utilization of distributed resources over a large data and they can access remotely through the net.

Background

Amazon web Service (AWS) started in the year 2006. Also Google and IBM have started research projects in cloud computing. Eucalyptus became the first open source platform for deploying private clouds [4].

Cloud Architecture

Cloud computing system is divided into two sections: the front end and the back end. Front end through which user can interact with the server and backend is the server which provides data to the client. Between server and client network is working as middleware.

Layers and Services of Cloud Computing Architecture

The below diagram shows the different layers of cloud Computing architecture [3].

Figure 1. Layers and services of Cloud Computing

A cloud client consists of computer hardware and/or computer software which relies on cloud computing for application delivery, or that is specifically designed for delivery of cloud services [9]. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is also referred as Resource Code, provide (managed and scalable) resources as services to the user in other words, they basically provide enhanced virtualization capabilities. Accordingly, different resources may be provided via a service interface [5]. Platform as a Service (PaaS) is provides computational resources via a platform upon which applications and services can be developed and hosted. Example: Google Docs, SAP business by design [5]. Software as a Service (SaaS) is also sometimes referred to as Service or application clouds. These clouds are offering implementation of specific business functions and business processes that are provided with specific cloud capabilities, i.e. they provide applications/services using a cloud infrastructure or platform, rather than providing cloud features themselves [5].

Deployment of Cloud Computing Service

For deploying a cloud computing solution, the major task is to decide on the type of cloud to be implemented. There are 3 fundamental Deployment Models of cloud computing: Public Cloud, Private Cloud and Hybrid Cloud. Figure below shows the overview of the deployment of these three clouds [6]: In Public Cloud model, services and infrastructure are hosted on premise of cloud provider and are provisioned for open use by general public. The end users can access the services via public network like internet. Public Cloud services are delivered mostly on demand. Popular for hosting everyday apps like email, CRM and other business support apps.

Public Cloud model offers high scalability, automated maintenance but more vulnerable to attacks due to high levels of accessibility. Common Public Cloud providers include Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure. You can even check out the details of Azure with the Azure Course.

Figure 2. Deployment of Cloud Services

Private Cloud model provides cloud services and infrastructure exclusively to a single tenant. The tenant can control and customize it to his need. The cloud infrastructure can be monitored either by cloud provider or the tenant. Many companies are migrating their data centers to Private Cloud to run core business fields like research, manufacturing human resource etc. The Private Cloud model offers great levels of security and control, though cost benefits ought to be sacrificed to some extent. As the name suggests Hybrid Cloud is composition of both Public Cloud and Private Cloud infrastructure. The company can use Private Cloud to run mission critical operations and Private Cloud to run non sensitive high demand operations. The companies using Hybrid Cloud model benefit with the security and control aspect of Private Cloud and off-hand management and cost benefits of

Public Cloud. Community cloud is constructed by many organizations and institutions according to their requirements. Cloudinfrastructure is managed by third party or one of the organizations

Advantages and Disadvantages of Cloud Computing

Advantages

- 1) Easy to Maintain.
- 2) Minimal cost
- 3) Pay as on demand.
- 4) Personalized Backup and recovery.
- 5) Remote access.
- 6) Greenly computing.

Disadvantages

- 1) Security and privacy.
- 2) Comparatively Higher operational cost.

2) Virtualization

Virtualization is the process of running a virtual instance of a computer system in a layer abstracted from the actual hardware. Most commonly, it refers to running multiple operating systems on a computer system simultaneously. To the applications running on top of the virtualized machine, it can appear as if they are on their own dedicated machine, where the operating system, libraries, and other programs are unique to the guest virtualized system and unconnected to the host operating system which sits below it. [8].

Types of Virtualization

- 1) Full virtualization (Native virtualization):

Full Virtualization was introduced by IBM in the year 1966. It is the first software solution for server virtualization and uses binary translation and direct approach techniques. In full virtualization, guest OS is completely isolated by the virtual machine from the virtualization layer and hardware. Microsoft and Parallels systems are examples of full virtualization.

- 2) Para virtualization:

Para virtualization is the category of CPU virtualization which uses hyper calls for operations to handle instructions at compile time. In para virtualization, guest OS is not completely isolated but it is partially isolated by the virtual machine from the virtualization layer and hardware. Examples are Microsoft Hyper-V and VMware ESX Server.

Load Balancing

A) What is Load Balancing?

Load Balancing is a technique in which the workload on the resources of a node is shifts to respective resources on the other node in a network without disturbing the running task. A standard way to scale web applications is by using a hardware-based load balancer [9]. The load balancer assumes the IP address of the web application, so all communication with the web for processing. The hardware-based load balancer is designed to handle high-level of load, so it can easily scale [10]. However, a hardware-based load balancer uses application specific hardware-based components, thus it is typically expensive. Because of cloud's commodity business model, a hardware-based load balancer is rarely occurred by cloud providers as a service. Instead, one has to use a software based load balancer running on a generic server [10].

B) Goals of Load balancing

As given in [12], the goals of load balancing are:

- 1) To improvise the performance substantially.
- 2) To have a backup plan in case the system fails partially or fully.
- 3) To maintain the system stableness.

- 4) To accommodate future modification in the system.

C) Types of Load Balancing Algorithms

1) Static Algorithms:

Static load balancing is the method of dividing the incoming load on a server using algorithms that have prior information about the existing servers in the distributed network. These load balancing schemes have a pre-defined load schedule that determines a fixed amount of load that can be shed on other systems. [11].

2) Dynamic Algorithms:

It is a more versatile scheme of load balancing which can dynamically identify the amount of load that needs to be shed during runtime and which system should bear the load. [11].

D) Existing Load Balancing Techniques in Clouds

Following load balancing techniques are currently prevalent in clouds.

Vector Dot- A. Singh et al. [13] proposed a novel load balancing algorithm called Vector Dot. It handles the hierarchical complexity of the data-center and multidimensionality of resource loads across servers, network switches, and storage in an agile data center that has integrated server and storage virtualization technologies. CARTON- R. Stanojevic et al. [14] proposed a mechanism CARTON for cloud control that unifies the use of LB and DRL. LB (Load Balancing) is used to equally distribute the jobs to different servers so that the associated costs can be minimized and DRL (Distributed Rate Limiting) is used to make sure that the resources are distributed in a way to keep a fair resource allocation. Compare and Balance- Y. Zhao et al. [15] addressed the problem of intra-cloud load balancing amongst physical hosts by adaptive live migration of virtual machines. A load balancing model is designed and implemented to reduce virtual machines' migration time by shared storage, to balance load amongst servers according to their processor or IO usage, etc. and to keep virtual machines' zero-downtime in the process. Event-driven- V. Nae et al. [16] presented an event driven load balancing algorithm for real-time Massively Multiplayer Online Games (MMOG). This algorithm after receiving capacity events as input, analysis its components in context of the resources and the global state of the game session, thereby generating the game session load balancing actions. Scheduling strategy on LB of VM resources – J. Hu et al. [17] proposed a scheduling strategy on load balancing of VM resources that uses historical data and current state of the system. This strategy achieves the best load balancing and reduced dynamic migration by using a genetic algorithm. CLBVM- A. Bhadani et al. [18] proposed a Central Load Balancing Policy for Virtual Machines (CLBVM) that balances the load evenly in a distributed virtual machine/cloud computing environment. LBVS- H. Liu et al. [19] proposed a load balancing virtual storage strategy (LBVS) that provides a large scale net data storage model and Storage as a Service model based on Cloud Storage. Storage virtualization is achieved using an architecture that is three-layered and load balancing is achieved using two load balancing modules. It helps in improving the efficiency. Task Scheduling based on LB- Y. Fang et al. discussed a two-level task scheduling mechanism based on load balancing to meet dynamic requirements of users and obtain high resource utilization. It achieves load balancing by first mapping tasks to virtual machines and then virtual machines to host resources thereby improving the task response time, resource utilization and overall performance of the cloud computing environment. Honeybee Foraging Behavior- M. Randles et al. [21] investigated a decentralized honeybee-based load balancing technique that is a nature-inspired algorithm for self-organization. It achieves global load balancing through local server actions. Performance of the system is enhanced with increased system diversity but throughput is not increased with an increase in system size. It is best suited for the conditions where the diverse population of service types is required. Biased Random Sampling- M. Randles et al. investigated a distributed and scalable load balancing approach that uses random sampling of the system domain to achieve self-organization thus balancing the load across all nodes of the system. Active Clustering- M. Randles et al. [21] investigated a self-aggregation load balancing technique that is a self-aggregation algorithm to optimize job assignments by connecting similar services using local re-wiring. The performance of the system is enhanced with high resources thereby increasing the throughput by using these resources effectively. It is degraded with an increase in system diversity. ACCLB- Z. Zhang et al. [22] proposed a load balancing mechanism based on ant colony and complex network theory (ACCLB) in an open cloud computing federation. It uses small-world and scale-free characteristics of a complex network to achieve better load balancing. This technique overcomes heterogeneity, is adaptive to dynamic environments, is excellent in fault tolerance and has good scalability hence helps in improving the performance of the system. (OLB + LBMM)- S.-C. [24] Proposed a new content aware

load balancing policy named as work-load and client aware policy (WCAP). It uses a parameter named as USP to specify the unique and special property of the requests as well as computing nodes. USP helps the scheduler to decide the best suitable node for processing the requests. Join-Idle-Queue- Y. Lua et al. [25] proposed a Join-Idle-Queue load balancing algorithm for dynamically scalable web services. This algorithm provides large-scale load balancing with distributed dispatchers by, first load balancing idle processors across dispatchers for the availability of idle processors at each dispatcher and then, assigning jobs to processors to reduce average queue length at each processor.

Conclusion

We have survey load balancing. In cloud computing load balancing is the main issue. Because when client is requesting for service it should be available to the client. When node is overloaded with job at that time load balancer has to set that load on another free node.so, to balance the load is necessary in cloud computing.

References

- [1] John Harauz, Lorti M. Kaufinan. Bruce Potter, "Data Security in the World of Cloud Computing", IEEE Security & Privacy, Copublished by the IEEE Computer and Reliability Societies, July/August 2009.
- [2] National Institute of Standards and Technology- Computer Security Resource Center -www.csrc.nist.gov
- [3] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_computing.
- [4] Yashpalsinh Jadeja and Kirit Modi, "Cloud Computing - Concepts, Architecture and Challenges", International Conference on Computing, Electronics and Electrical Technologies [ICCEET], IEEE-2012.
- [5] Samerjeet kaur, "Cryptography and Encryption in Cloud Computing", VSRD International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, VSRD- IJCSIT, Vol. 2 (3), 2012.
- [6] Ramgovind S, Eloff MM, Smith E, "The management of security in cloud computing", IEEE – 2010.
- [7] Aderemi A. Atayero and Oluwaseyi Feyisetan," Security Issues in Cloud Computing: The Potentials of Homomorphic Encryption" Journal of Emerging Trends in Computing and Information Sciences, VOL. 2, NO. 10, October 2011.
- [8] Turban, E; King, D; Lee, J; Viehland," Chapter 19: Building E-Commerce Applications and Infrastructure". Electronic Commerce A Managerial Perspective. pp. 27, 2008.
- [9] J. Kruskal and M. Liberman."The Symmetric Time Warping Problem: From Continuous to Discrete. In Time Warps, String Edits and Macromolecules: The Theory and Practice of Sequence Comparison", pp. 125-161, Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., 1983.
- [10]Mr. Nitin S. More, Mrs. Swapnaja R. Hiray and Mrs. Smita Shukla Patel," Load Balancing and Resource Monitoring in Cloud", International Journal of Advances in Computing and Information Researches ISSN: 2277- 4068, Volume 1– No.2, April 2012.
- [11]R. X. T. and X. F. Z,"A Load Balancing Strategy Based on the Combination of Static and Dynamic, in Database Technology and Applications (DBTA)",2nd International Workshop,2010.
- [12]David Escalante and Andrew J. Korty, "Cloud Services: Policy and Assessment", EDUCAUSE Review, vol. 46, no. 4 (July/August 2011).
- [13]Singh A., Korupolu M. and Mohapatra D., ACM/IEEE conference on Supercomputing, 2008.
- [14]Stanojevic R. and Shorten R., IEEE ICC, 1-6, 2009.
- [15]Zhao Y. and Huang W., 5th International Joint Confer-ence on INC, IMS and IDC, 170-175, 2009.
- [16]Nae V., Prodan R. and Fahringer T., 11th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Grid Computing (Grid), 9-17,2010.
- [17]Hu J., Gu J., Sun G. and Zhao T., 3rd International Symposium on Parallel Architectures, Algorithms and Programming, 89-96, 2010.
- [18]Bhadani A. and Chaudhary S., 3rd Annual ACM Bangalore Conference, 2010.
- [19]Liu H., Liu S., Meng X., Yang C. and Zhang Y.,International Conference on Service Sciences (ICSS), 257-262,2010.

TECHNO-PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

The present study is entitled as “Techno-pedagogical skills among student teachers”. Techno-pedagogy is a significant deciding aspect for the mixture approach of reflective teaching. The last two decennials have witnessed the inclusion of progresses in techno-pedagogical skills in higher education organizations around the world. Use of techno-pedagogical skills can break down some of the barriers that lead to underachievement, student disillusionment and educational barring. Every student teacher must know how to utilize technology, pedagogy and subject area content effectively in their classroom teaching. It is clear that merely presenting technology to the educational process is not sufficient. One must ensure technological integration meanwhile technology by itself will not lead to change. Rather, it is the way in which student teachers integrate technology that has the potential to bring change in the education system. The research type was a survey method, which consists of random sampling of 30 student teachers in Tirunelveli district. Personal data sheet was prepared by the investigator and techno-pedagogical skills of student teachers scale was prepared and validated by Sibichen and Annaraja (2009). The interpretation of data was done with statistical methods in percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation and ‘t’-test.

Keywords: *Techno-Pedagogical Skills and Student Teachers*

Introduction

Teaching is not only confined to impart knowledge of subject matter to others. In a wider perspective, teaching aims at an all-round development of personality. Skills or attitudes can be developed through systematic training. A systematized knowledge is required in order to achieve these skills and attitudes which require training (Kakkad, 1988). Teacher education is not teaching the teacher to teach, but it is to learn to teach and teach to learn. Teacher education is a process aiming at the formation of positive attitudes towards teaching profession. So, a sound programme for professional education of teachers is essential for the quality improvement in education (Aggarwal, 1985). Techno-pedagogical method of teaching in which ICT is being integrated for teaching learning process. It describes, ‘pedagogy’ refers to the art-science of teaching and ‘techno’ refers to the art-skill in handcrafting. Here, ‘techno’ is a qualifier, it intersects or crosses the meaning of ‘pedagogy’ with its own. Techno-pedagogy refers to weaving the techniques of the craft of teaching into the learning environment itself.

Need and Significance of the Study

The value of technology in teaching and learning has been a subject of some contention in the education community for some time. Teachers’ use of technologies has an important role in education in the 21st century. Technology can provide powerful environments eliciting modern views of learning but may not change teachers’ beliefs and practice. It depends on how teachers interpret the uses of tools and how they use them to transform the learning processes (Riel, 1998). The advent of internet-based technology in the classroom acts as an impetus for the re-conceptualization of learning; the idea that ICT has the potential to transform teaching and learning is broadly held (UNESCO, 2002). Preparing future teachers who know how to integrate effective use of ICT in their curriculum remains a challenging goal for teacher preparation programmes. In order to increase the technology proficiency of new teachers in classrooms, training institutions should increase the level of technology integration in their own academic programmes. Technologies seem to help student teachers overcome a great array of teaching challenges or difficulties encountered during their teaching. The greatest advantage of using technologies appears to be the variety of activities that can be undertaken in the classrooms. Technology appears to help student teachers diversify both their teaching strategies and the activities they expect learners to accomplish. Being a student teacher this thought directs this researcher towards analyzing the techno-pedagogical skills among student teachers.

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Objectives

- 1) To find out the level of techno-pedagogical skills of student teachers.
- 2) To find out whether there is any significant difference in techno-pedagogical skills of student teachers with regard to gender.
- 3) To find out whether there is any significant difference in techno-pedagogical skills of student teachers with regard to location of student.

Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their techno-pedagogical skills.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their techno-pedagogical skills.

Delimitation

- 1) The study is limited to student teachers in Tirunelveli district only.
- 2) The investigator has proposed to choose only 30 student teachers as sample for the study.

Method Used

The investigator has adopted survey method to do a “Techno-pedagogical skills among student teachers”.

Population and Sample

The population of the present study consists of student teachers those who are studying in B.Ed., Colleges of Tirunelveli district, Tamil Nadu. The investigator has used simple random sampling technique for selecting the sample from the population. The sample consists of 30 student teachers. Among them 15 were male and 15 were female student teachers.

Tool Used

This study aims to evaluate the techno-pedagogical skills among student teachers. The investigator has adopted the techno-pedagogical skill assessment scale developed and validated by Sibichen and Annaraja (2009).

Statistics Techniques Used

Percentage analysis and ‘t’ test were used in this study.

Analysis of Data

Table 1 Level of Techno-Pedagogical Skills of Student Teachers

Dimensions	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Learning	7	23.3	18	60.0	5	16.7
Preparing Lesson	2	6.7	23	76.7	5	16.7
Preparing learning material	5	16.7	19	63.3	6	20.0
Implementing instructional strategy	6	20.0	20	66.7	4	13.3
Communication	5	16.7	22	73.3	3	10.0
Evaluation	3	10.0	24	80.0	3	10.0
Guidance	3	10.0	22	73.3	5	16.7
Overall Techno Pedagogical Skill	5	16.7	20	66.7	5	16.7

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Table – 2 Difference between Male and Female Student Teachers in their Techno-Pedagogical Skills

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
Learning	Male	15	17.60	2.640	1.110	NS
	Female	15	18.87	3.543		
Preparing Lesson	Male	15	17.87	1.727	0.275	NS
	Female	15	17.53	4.373		
Preparing learning material	Male	15	17.73	2.987	0.993	NS
	Female	15	16.40	4.256		
Implementing instructional strategy	Male	15	17.73	2.604	0.573	NS
	Female	15	18.33	3.109		
Communication	Male	15	19.07	4.250	0.259	NS
	Female	15	19.47	4.224		
Evaluation	Male	15	18.80	2.883	0.935	NS
	Female	15	17.60	4.050		
Guidance	Male	15	18.33	1.799	1.969	S
	Female	15	16.53	3.091		
Overall Techno Pedagogical Skill	Male	15	127.13	12.305	0.383	NS
	Female	15	124.73	20.937		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96, S - Significant NS - Not Significant)

Table – 3 Difference between Rural and Urban Student Teachers in their Techno-Pedagogical Skills

Dimensions	Location of Student	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
Learning	Rural	21	17.05	2.559	3.786	S
	Urban	9	21.00	2.646		
Preparing Lesson	Rural	21	16.71	2.552	2.405	S
	Urban	9	20.00	3.742		
Preparing learning material	Rural	21	15.86	3.291	3.262	S
	Urban	9	19.89	3.018		
Implementing instructional strategy	Rural	21	17.52	2.379	1.310	NS
	Urban	9	19.22	3.563		
Communication	Rural	21	18.48	4.203	1.791	NS
	Urban	9	21.11	3.655		
Evaluation	Rural	21	17.48	3.586	1.979	S
	Urban	9	19.89	2.804		
Guidance	Rural	21	17.14	2.594	0.886	NS
	Urban	9	18.11	2.804		
Overall Techno	Rural	21	120.24	14.121	3.086	S

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Pedagogical Skill	Urban	9	139.22	15.975		
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(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96, S - Significant NS - Not Significant)

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reveals that the level of techno pedagogical skill and its dimensions of student teachers. In this level 16.7% of students teachers have high level of leaning, 16.7% of students teachers have high level of preparing lesson, 20.0% of students teachers have high level of preparing learning material, 10.0% of students teachers have high level of implementing instructional strategy, 10.0% of students teachers have high level of communication, 10.0% of students teachers have high level of evaluation, 16.7% of students teachers have high level of guidance and 16.7% of students teachers have high level of overall techno pedagogical skill.

The table 2 reveals that there is a significant difference between male and female student teachers in their guidance. While comparing the mean scores male student teachers are better than the female student teachers. But there is no significant difference between male and female student teachers in their leaning, preparing lesson, preparing learning material, implementing instructional strategy, communication, evaluation and overall techno pedagogical skill. This may due to the fact that male student teachers find it easy to interact with students and identify the needy ones and make extra effort to associate with problem children and take it as a challenge over and above their counter parts.

The table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their leaning, preparing lesson, preparing learning material, evaluation and overall techno pedagogical skill. While comparing the mean scores urban student teachers are better than the rural student teachers. But there is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers in their implementing instructional strategy, communication and guidance. This may due to the fact that urban students have more exposure to have a better relationship with technological resources and it will lead them to better learning and preparing learning material and evaluation and overall pedagogical skills.

Recommendations

Educational Technology (ET) and ICT in education should be offered as core courses at the teacher education programme, especially female student teacher. Refresher courses, workshop should be conducted on educational technology and ICT to rural student teachers. Digital lesson planning and implementation should be promoted in all the teacher education institutions, particularly rural and female student teachers.

References

- [1] Aggarwal, (1985). The management of manufacturing operations: An appraisal of recent developments. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 5(3), 21-38. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb054741>
- [2] Kakkad, G.M. (1988). *Secondary teacher education*. Bombay: Himalaya Publishing House.
- [3] Riel, (1998). *Prophet of the new world*. Canada: Good read Biographies, Halifax.
- [4] Sibichen, K. K. & Annaraja, P. (2011). *Techno_pedagogical and thinking skills of the secondary teacher education students*, Department of Education, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University. Published Ph.D. dissertation, St. Xavier's College of Education, Palayamkottai. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/133909>
- [5] UNESCO (2002). *Education for All: Is the World on Track? EFA Global Monitoring Report*. Paris.

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON GENDER AND LOCALITY OF STUDENTS IN RESPECT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ISSUES

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Abstract

An investigation made on influence of social media on gender and locality of students in respect of psychological issues like depression, anxiety, addiction, Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying and cognitive development. The tool is standardized by item analysis. The data is collected by stratified random sampling technique with a sample size of 630 students, by using interview cum survey method. Mean, SD, t test and f-ratio statistical technique are used on collected data for finding results and interpretation purpose. It is found that there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that there is a no significant difference among boys and girls on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students of Kurnool district, but there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district. There is a no significant difference among urban and rural on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber , addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district.

Keywords: *Depression, Anxiety, Cyber Bullying, Students, Social Media.*

Introduction

Social media are interactive technologies that make it easier to create and share content across virtual communities and networks, including information, ideas, hobbies, and other kinds of expression (Kietzmann, 2011), (Obar, 2015). Although there are difficulties with the definition of social media since there are so many standalone and integrated social media services now, there are certain similar characteristics (Obar, 2015: Social media are Web 2.0 Internet-based interactive apps (Obar, 2015), (Kaplan Andreas., 2010), User-generated material is the lifeblood of social media, including written posts or comments, digital photographs or videos, and data created via all online interactions. (Obar, 2015), (Kaplan Andreas., 2010), Users build profiles for the website or app that are created and managed by the social media company and are service-specific (Obar, 2015), (Boyd., 2007) and Social media facilitates the growth of online social networks by tying a user's profile to that of other people or organisations (Obar, 2015), (Boyd., 2007). In relation to media, the word "social" implies that platforms are user-centric and encourage social interaction. Social media may thus be seen as an online facilitator or enhancer of human networks—networks of people that improve social connection (Dijck, 2013). Typically, users access social media services using web-based desktop applications or by downloading apps for their mobile devices (e.g., smartphones and tablets). Users who connect with these digital services build highly interactive platforms on which people, groups, and organisations may exchange, co-create, converse about, participate in, and change user-generated or self-curated material that is published online (Schivinski, 2020), (Boy, 2007), (Dennis, 2017). The present study is on the influence of social media on gender and locality of students in respect of psychological issues.

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Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy.

Fig 1 : Sample Design

Tools

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the Psychological impact of Social Media on high School Students at Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.
- 2) To find out the psychological impact of social media on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district

Hypothesis

- 1) There would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district.
- 2) There would be no significant difference between psychological impact of social media on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district

Fig 2. Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Gender and Locality

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Results and Discussion

Table 1: Means, SD's and t- values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Gender.

S.No	Scheme	Gender	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Depression	Boys	271	14.63	4.47	0.3365@
		Girls	359	14.51	4.38	
2	Addiction	Boys	271	24.39	5.09	5.7744**
		Girls	359	26.89	5.79	
3	Anxiety	Boys	271	10.59	3.30	0.9203@
		Girls	359	10.35	3.16	
4	Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying	Boys	271	18.29	4.45	1.2830@
		Girls	359	18.77	4.90	
5	Cognitive (Knowledge) Development	Boys	271	72.49	14.49	4.3532**
		Girls	359	77.56	14.45	
6	Over All	Boys	271	140.84	22.45	4.2115**
		Girls	359	148.81	24.86	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630, as shown in figure 3 and table 1. In depression psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 14.67 and 4.47. similarly the girls are 14.51 and 4.38. The mean values of boys are slightly high in comparison to girls. The t value is 0.3365, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

In addiction psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 24.39 and 5.09. similarly the girls are 26.89 and 5.79. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 5.7744, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In anxiety psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 10.59 and 3.30. similarly the girls are 10.35 and 3.16. The mean values of boys are slightly high in comparison to girls. The t value is 0.9203, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

In social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 18.29 and 4.45, similarly the girls are 18.77 and 4.49. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 1.2839, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In cognitive development psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 72.49 and 14.49. similarly the girls are 77.56 and 14.45. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 4.3532, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

In over all psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 140.84 and 22.45. similarly the girls are 148.81 and 24.86. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 4.2115, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630.

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Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

Fig 3 Mean and SD values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Gender.

Table 2: Means, SD's and t- values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Locality

S.No	Scheme	Locality	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Depression	Urban	143	14.47	4.36	0.4565@
		Rural	487	14.60	4.473	
2	Addiction	Urban	143	26.04	5.82	0.5474@
		Rural	487	25.74	5.56	
3	Anxiety	Urban	143	10.44	3.79	0.1285@
		Rural	487	10.40	3.21	
4	Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying	Urban	143	18.66	4.91	0.2388@
		Rural	487	18.54	4.66	
5	Cognitive (Knowledge) Development	Urban	143	75.48	14.33	0.1019@
		Rural	487	75.34	14.79	
6	Over All	Urban	143	145.66	24.74	0.1451@
		Rural	487	145.32	24.01	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level

* indicates significant at 0.05 level

@ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The psychological impact of social media on urban and rural of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of urban and rural are 143 and 487. The total no of students are 630, as shown in figure 4 and table 2. In depression psychological factor the mean and SD values of urban are 14.67 and 4.47. similarly the rural are 14.47 and 4.36. The mean values rural are slightly high in comparison to urban. The t value is 0.4565, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In anxiety psychological factor the mean and SD values of urban are 10.44 and 3.79. similarly

the rural are 10.40 and 3.21. The mean values of urban are slightly high in comparison to rural. The t value is 0.1285, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor the mean and SD values of urban are 18.66 and 4.91, similarly the rural are 18.54 and 4.66. In over all psychological factor the mean and SD values of urban are 145.66 and 24.74 similarly the rural are 145.33 and 24.01. The mean values of rural are slightly high in comparison to urban. The t value is 0.1451, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that there is a no significant difference among urban and rural on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber, addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district.

Fig 4. Mean and SD values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Locality

Conclusion

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. . Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

References

- [1] Kietzmann, Jan H.; Kristopher Hermkens (2011). "Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media". *Business Horizons* (Submitted manuscript). 54 (3): 241–251. doi:10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.005. S2CID 51682132
- [2] Obar, Jonathan A.; Wildman, Steve (2015). "Social media definition and the governance challenge: An introduction to the special issue". *Telecommunications Policy*. 39 (9): 745–750. doi:10.2139/ssrn.2647377. SSRN 2647377.
- [3] Dennis, Amy (July 5, 2017). "5 Social Media Outlets Ruling the World". Nice Branding Agency. Retrieved October 10, 2021.

MOOCs : The Future Prospect

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Abstract

Massive open online courses (MOOCs) are one of the latest trends of learning in higher education in recent years. A massive open online course (MOOC) is a model for delivering and learning content online to anyone who wants to take a course, with no limit on attendance with usually free of cost. Conventional online courses require tuition fee to learn, carry credit and limit enrolment to a few dozens to ensure interaction with interaction, on the other hand, massive open online courses are available to any person is usually free, credit less and massive too. Talking about MOOCs, MOOCs are excellent for promoting lifelong learning. They potentially offer much flexibility for people who want to complete their training in a particular subject or who want to gain new knowledge in a specific area. This study discussed the advantage of MOOCs and how it becomes a boon to all the students, learners, skill developers and information seekers.

Introduction

A massive open online course or an open online course is an online course aimed at unlimited participation and open access via the Web. In addition to traditional course materials, such as filmed lectures, readings, and problem sets, many MOOCs provide interactive courses with user forums or social media discussions to support community interactions among students, professors, and teaching assistants, as well as immediate feedback to quick quizzes and assignments. MOOCs are a widely researched development in distance education, first introduced in 2008, that emerged as a popular mode of learning in 2012, a year called the "Year of the MOOC".

Types of MOOC

MOOCs can either be: Synchronous, which means everyone on the course is following the same elements or modules of the course at the same time, or Asynchronous, which means that people can enter and follow the course at any time so that at any one time some people will be just starting the course whilst others may be part way through or even finishing the course. There are considered to be two different types of MOOCs: cMOOCs, which are connective Massive Open Online Courses that share digital online learning elements and environments and are connected together in a variety of ways. xMOOCs, or extended Massive Open Online Courses. xMOOCs tend to be based on content provided by universities and other educational institutions that provide significant research-based content and background in the online learning content. I submit they are yet to wreak their full vengeance on the education industry.

Offer a Variety of Subjects

College schedules are tight, so you might not be able to take every course that you want to. Your college may not even offer a subject that you're interested in. This is where MOOCs can help. Search on one of the MOOC providers' websites to find interesting classes. The subjects range from yoga to personal finance to engineering to IT to English composition, etc.

Let You Test Out Your Major Before Committing

In most cases, the major chosen by the high school students heavily influences the college you attend and your future career path. High school students can complete a MOOC course in their prospective major to see if it's the right fit. This risk-free, money-free method will help the students to figure out what major to choose and ultimately save you money. Students may won't waste time bouncing between majors and paying for useless classes.

Familiarize Learners with College-Level Learning Before Enrolling

Wondering if college learning is right for you? Taking a MOOC will help the students to understand what college classes are like before paying for them. The tests and assignments completed by the students offer insight into what the next four years might look like. If possible, try out a course at a college you're considering attending.

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Prepare the Students Academically for College

In 2010, nearly 70% of high school seniors accepted to college were unprepared. Many MOOCs are designed to help combat this unpreparedness. Some MOOCs for high school students include entry-level math, first-year composition, and pre-calculus. Talk to your guidance counselor or teachers to see what areas they recommend you focus on.

Learn from Peers Around the World

Anyone from any country with internet access can take a MOOC class. Participants can communicate with one another through discussion threads and social networking. Just like in a real classroom, you'll learn from your peers and possibly broaden your worldview too.

They're Open to Everyone

Another one of the advantages of MOOCs is that there are no prerequisites for MOOC learning. You can sign up for any class no matter your background or age. Just be prepared to put in the effort.

Anytime, Anywhere Access

MOOCs, being online, can be accessed anytime from anywhere. Students no longer need to travel to the institute or be on time to attend a lecture. There is no fear of missing a lecture if someone is not able to travel or not in a position to attend a live lecture.

Frees Up Teachers' Time

Teachers don't need to give the same lecture again and again, they can focus on resolving queries and helping students. This in turn also helps students utilize contact time with teachers in a more meaningful way and get personal attention.

Cost Savings

The biggest advantage of MOOCs is perhaps the cost factor. Anyone can get a full-fledged graduate certification from a premier institute at half (or less) the cost compared to an on-campus course. This is in addition to travel and accommodation and other costs. This certainly makes education more accessible.

Premier Institute Opportunity

All physical institutes have very limited seats. MOOCs open up the barrier and can allow many students who would not get to study in those institutes.

Moocs Are Available In Different Languages

Your course options aren't restricted just based on where you live. Enjoy courses taught in foreign countries without hesitation thanks to subtitles. Subtitles also make these courses friendly to individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing.

Learning at Your Own Pace, Following your Own Schedule.

Some of the courses have deadlines for tests and assessments, but they are easy to keep. Usually one have weeks to finish the quizzes and it is not seldom the case that learners have the option to finish a course whenever they feel like it, whenever they have the time. In other words learning happens in a more informal setting, at a place of your convenience and often around your own schedule.

Offer Free Ap Exam Preparation and Courses

Harvard University and MIT's edX MOOC platform offers FREE AP exam preparation and courses. Learners can learn confusing material at your own pace outside of your high school classroom. These supplementary courses will help you achieve high AP exam scores that in turn will give you college credit.

Help Your College And Scholarship Applications Stand Out

Anything learner can do in high school to show future college admissions counselors that you're serious about learning will help your application. Knowledge gained from MOOCs will also help in department or interest-specific scholarship applications and interviews. Plus, taking these massive open online courses shows

initiative and intellectual curiosity. These are both characteristics of a successful student.

Boost Your Job Applications and Career Prospects

Employers look for several soft skills in their future employees. Some degree programs help students develop these skills better than others do. Free online college classes like MOOCs help bridge the gap between college graduate and employee. edX provides several free “soft skills” courses that cover topics from teamwork to public speaking. This MOOC platform also offers paid professional programs that are certified. Their Soft Skills professional certificate program by Rochester Institute of Technology includes 6 courses and costs \$49 per course. You can also opt to take their professional courses free without the certification.

Distributed Learning.

Participants help each other interpret the material, seek out different or related sources, and use social networking to share their interpretations. Through this distributed learning, participants gain a better understanding of the material and can get immediate feedback if questions arise.

Conclusion

With the advent of technology, e-learning is rapidly gaining importance and momentum. With the government aiming at digitising India with its „Digital India“ initiative, educational institutes are also working in tandem to help fulfil the goal. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) are fast gaining popularity among students and working professionals as they help them study at their convenience and time. Websites such as edX and Coursera enlist free online courses from various institutes across the world. Such is the popularity of MOOCs that last year Prime Minister Modi launched „SWAYAM“, a MOOC platform in India, which will have two courses from the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, and one from Princeton University, U.S. The courses can be accessed free of cost. Today, several other Indian institutes have collaborated with SWAYAM and many more courses are on offer.

References

- [1] Bersin Josh (2013), The MOOC Marketplace Takes Off, Retrieved from Forbes on January 9th, 2023: <http://www.forbes.com/sites/joshbersin/2013/11/30/the-mooc-marketplace-takes-off/>
- [2] Dodd Tim (2015), Fee payments lift MOOC completion rates, Retrieved from AFRWeekend on Jan 9th, 2023: <http://www.afr.com/news/policy/education/fee-payments-lift-mooc-completion-rates-20150412-1mhw76>
- [3] Lackner E., & Kopp, M., (2014), Do MOOCs need a special Instructional Design?, Retrieved on January 9th, 2023 from: http://www.researchgate.net/publication/263784897_Do_MOOCs_need_a_Special_Instructional_Design
- [4] LeBar Matthew, (2014), MOOCs --Completion is not important, Retrieved from Forbes on Jan 9th, 2023: <http://www.forbes.com/sites/ccap/2014/09/16/moocs-finishing-is-not-the-important-part/>
- [5] National University Technology Network (2014), MOOCs Next Phase: Global system for MOOCs Verified Credential Recognition, Retrieved on Jan 9th, 2023 from <http://www.slideshare.net/MOOCsUniversity/moocs-next-phase-global-central-system-for-credential-recognition>
- [6] Parr Chris (2013), MOOC Completion Rates „below 7%“: Open online courses“ cohort much less massive at finish line, Retrieved from Times Higher Education on Jan 9th, 2023: <https://www.timeshighereducation.co.uk/news/mooc-completion-rates-below-7/2003710.article>
- [7] Shah Dhawal (2014), MOOCs in 2014: Breaking down the numbers, Retrieved from edSurge on Jan 9th, 2023: <https://www.edsurge.com/n/2014-12-26-moocs-in-2014-breaking-down-the-numbers>
- [8] Wikipedia (2023), Massive Open Online Course, Retrieved on January 10th, 2023 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Massive_open_online_courses

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: NEED OF THE HOUR

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Abstract

Inclusive education values diversity and the unique contributions each student brings to the classroom. In a truly inclusive setting, every child feels safe and has a sense of belonging. They enjoy field trips and after-school activities together. They participate in student government together and attend the same sports meets and plays. Each Student benefit is the cornerstone of inclusive education. Common learning environments are used for the majority of the students' regular instruction hours and may include classrooms, libraries, gym, performance theatres, music rooms, cafeterias, playgrounds and the local community. A common learning environment is not a place where students with intellectual disabilities or other special needs learn in isolation from their peers.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Students With Disabilities (SWD), Inclusive Classroom*

Introduction

School is a place fondly remembered for sparking their passion or connecting to them to a favorite mentor. Classroom discrimination can take many forms and have serious impacts on learning. inclusive education solutions addresses the inequities faced by vulnerable populations to improve their learning and employment outcomes ensuring that no one gets left behind.

Inclusive Education

Around the world, children are excluded from schools where they belong because of disability, race, language, religion, gender, and poverty. Inclusive education means different and diverse students learning side by side in the same classroom. And school staffs have the training, support, flexibility, and resources to nurture, encourage, and respond to the needs of all students. Inclusive education is about ensuring access to quality education for all students by effectively meeting their diverse needs in a way that is responsive, accepting, respectful and supportive. Students participate in the education program in a common learning environment with support to diminish and remove barriers and obstacles that may lead to exclusion. Inclusive education is carried out in a common learning environment; that is, an educational setting where students from different backgrounds and with different abilities learn together in an inclusive environment.

Key Features of Inclusive Education

Important features and practices are:

- 1)Accepting unconditionally all children into regular classes and the life of the school.
- 2)Providing as much support to children, teachers and classrooms as necessary to ensure that all children can participate in their schools and classes.
- 3)Looking at all children at what they can do rather than what they cannot do.
- 4)Teachers and parents have high expectations of all children.
- 5)Developing education goals according to each child's abilities. This means that children do not need to have the same education goals in order to learn together in regular classes.
- 6)Designing schools and classes in ways that help children learn and achieve to their fullest potential. Having strong leadership for inclusion from school principals and other administrators.
- 7)Having teachers who have knowledge about different ways of teaching so that children with various abilities and strengths can learn together.
- 8)Having principals, teachers, parents and others work together to determine the most effective ways of providing a quality education in an inclusive environment.

Inclusive Classroom Strategies

There is a definite need for teachers to be supported in implementing an inclusive classroom. Most teachers had either neutral or negative attitudes about inclusive education. It turns out that much of this is because they do not feel they are very knowledgeable, competent, or confident about how to educate SWD. However, similar to parents, teachers with more experience and in the case of teachers, more training with inclusive education were significantly more positive about it. Teachers need an understanding of best practices in teaching and of adapted instruction for SWD. Positive attitudes toward inclusion are also among the most important for

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creating an inclusive classroom that works.

Use a Variety of Instructional Formats

Start with whole-group instruction and transition to flexible groupings which could be small groups, stations/centers, and paired learning. With regard to the whole group, using technology such as interactive whiteboards is related to high student engagement. Regarding flexible groupings: for younger students, these are often teacher-led but for older students, they can be student-led with teacher monitoring. Peer-supported learning can be very effective and engaging and take the form of pair-work, cooperative grouping, peer tutoring, and student-led demonstrations.

Ensure Access to Academic Curricular Content

All students need the opportunity to have learning experiences in line with the same learning goals. This will necessitate thinking about what supports individual SWDs need, but overall strategies are making sure all students hear instructions, that they do indeed start activities, that all students participate in large group instruction, and that student's transition in and out of the classroom at the same time.

Apply Universal Design for Learning

These are methods that are varied and that support many learners' needs. They include multiple ways of representing content to students and for students to represent learning back, such as modeling, images, objectives and manipulative, graphic organizers, oral and written responses, and technology. These can also be adapted as modifications for SWDs where they have large print, use headphones, are allowed to have a peer write their dictated response, draw a picture instead, use calculators, or just have extra time. Think too about the power of project-based and inquiry learning where students individually or collectively investigate an experience.

Common Practices in Inclusive Classrooms

Students in an inclusive classroom are generally placed with their chronological age-mates, regardless of whether the students are working above or below the typical academic level for their age. Also, to encourage a sense of belonging, emphasis is placed on the value of friendships. Teachers often nurture a relationship between a student with special needs and a same-age student without a special educational need. Another common practice is the assignment of a buddy to accompany a student with special needs at all times (for example in the cafeteria, on the playground, on the bus and so on). This is used to show students that a diverse group of people make up a community, that no one type of student is better than another, and to remove any barriers to a friendship that may occur if a student is viewed as "helpless." Such practices reduce the chance for elitism among students in later grades and encourage cooperation among groups.

Teachers use a number of techniques to help build classroom communities:

- 1) Using games designed to build community
- 2) Involving students in solving problems
- 3) Sharing songs and books that teach community
- 4) Openly dealing with individual differences by discussion
- 5) Assigning classroom jobs that build community
- 6) Teaching students to look for ways to help each other
- 7) Utilizing physical therapy equipment such as standing frames, so students who typically use wheelchairs can stand when the other students are standing and more actively participate in activities
- 8) Encouraging students to take the role of teacher and deliver instruction (e.g. read a portion of a book to a student with severe disabilities)
- 9) Focusing on the strength of a student with special needs
- 10) Create classroom checklists
- 11) Take breaks when necessary
- 12) Create an area for children to calm down
- 13) Organize student desk in groups
- 14) Create a self and welcoming environment
- 15) Set ground rules and stick with them
- 16) Help establish short-term goals
- 17) Design a multi-faced curriculum

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- 18) Communicate regular with parents and/or caregivers
- 19) Seek support from other special education teachers

Inclusionary Team-Teaching Models

One teach, one support: In this model, the content teacher will deliver the lesson and the special education teacher will assist students individual needs and enforce classroom management as needed. **One teach, one observe:** In this model, the teacher with the most experience in the content will deliver the lesson and the other teacher will float or observe. This model is commonly used for data retrieval during IEP observations or Functional Behavior Analysis. **Station teaching (rotational teaching):** In this model, the room is divided into stations in which the students will visit with their small groups. Generally, the content teacher will deliver the lesson in his/her group, and the special education teacher will complete a review or adapted version of the lesson with the students. **Parallel teaching:** In this model, one half of the class is taught by the content teacher and one half is taught by the special education teacher. Both groups are being taught the same lesson, just in a smaller group. **Alternative teaching:** In this method, the content teacher will teach the lesson to the class, while the special education teacher will teach a small group of students an alternative lesson. **Team teaching (content/support shared 50/50):** Both teachers share the planning, teaching, and supporting equally. This is the traditional method, and often the most successful co-teaching model.

The Benefits of Inclusive Education

Over the years, the benefits of providing an inclusive education to all children have been shown. Inclusive education (when practiced well) is very important because:

- 1) All children are able to be part of their community and develop a sense of belonging and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults.
- 2) It provides better opportunities for learning. Children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children.
- 3) The expectations of all the children are higher. Successful inclusion attempts to develop an individual's strengths and gifts.
- 4) It allows children to work on individual goals while being with other students their own age.
- 5) It encourages the involvement of parents in the education of their children and the activities of their local schools.
- 6) It fosters a culture of respect and belonging. It also provides the opportunity to learn about and accept individual differences.
- 7) It provides all children with opportunities to develop friendships with one another. Friendships provide role models and opportunities for growth.

Conclusion

Inclusion is also about finding different ways of teaching so that classrooms actively involve all children. It also means finding ways to develop friendships, relationships and mutual respect between all children, and between children and teachers in the school. Inclusive education is not just for some children. Being included is not something that a child must be ready for. All children are at all times ready to attend regular schools and classrooms. Their participation is not something that must be earned. As a value, inclusive education reflects the expectation that we want all of our children to be appreciated and accepted throughout life.

References

- [1] Taylor, S.J., Biklen, D. & Knoll, J. (1987). Community Integration for Persons with Severe Disabilities. NY, NY: Teachers College Press.
- [2] Florian, L. (ed.) 2007: The Sage Handbook of Special Education, London: Sage publications.
- [3] Hodkinson, A. & Vickerman, P. 2009: Key issues in special educational needs and inclusion. London: Sage publications.

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ROLE OF BLENDED LEARNING FOR HOLISTIC EDUCATION IN 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

Around the world, where traditional education system is transforming into the digital education landscape day by day, where blended learning plays a significant role in the teaching and learning process. The main purpose of this paper is to explore the role of blended learning in holistic education in the 21st century. An analysis of reviews shows that it was necessary to have a better ICT setup, competent expertise, a better budget, well-trained teachers, and a better technological infrastructure for blended learning to be implemented successfully in the classroom. The result of the study shows that blended learning is more effective, interesting, and inspiring for students as well as teachers. The conclusion of the study reveals that using online tools within the traditional classroom environment like projectors, smart boards, laptops, desktops, and some software applications during face-to-face teaching and learning sessions improved learner and teacher capabilities, interest, motivation, reasoning ability, learning potential, problem-solving skills, intellectual thinking, creativity, and cognitive power among the learners in teaching learning process. Furthermore, blended learning plays a major role in the development of education in 21st century. Blended education provides a better opportunity for enhancing the student's overall performance with their teaching and learning process.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Teaching, Learning Process, ICT, Online and Offline*

Introduction

In the process of teaching and learning, technology plays a vital role. The present development of technology is highly helpful in teaching learning process. Education and technology are the two words that make up educational technology. The process of learning and disseminating knowledge, skill, and attitudes is known as education. Technology includes both technical devices and methods. Technology is the techniques of science and methods of acquiring new knowledge related to technology and others field such as, arts, science and specifically professional courses. National Council for Educational Research and Training defined that educational technology as the means of three different things includes with development, application and evaluation. The first thing is strategies/techniques, second is system and the third one is aids to improve overall teaching learning process. International Commission on the Development of education state that educational technology is the cognitive and operational power that arrange, re-arrange and systematized the application in a scientific way for the institution apparatus and materials to enhance teaching learning process. In educational technology there are so many methods and techniques of learning such as, online learning, web-based learning, virtual classroom learning, flipped learning, ICT based constructivist learning, cooperative learning, online collaborative learning, project-based learning and one of them is blended learning. Current education system is rapidly change and transform into the digital literacy, after Covid-19 the education system is totally changed with the help of technology. Technology plays an important role in educational landscape. Blended approach is a holistic approach for the development of teachers and students in teaching learning process. It changes the traditional methods of teaching into the smart board, projectors, desktop, and mobile phones education, web based learning as well. Digital pedagogy is the latest trend for the current educational system and satisfies all needs for 21st century teaching and learning skills. The current academic environment demanded both fresh information and the use of several methodologies and technology.

Blended Learning

With the emergence of information communication technology some approaches of teaching and learning transform into the digital forms. The traditional methods such as lectures methods, chalk and duster methods are changing day by day in the form of integration technology in education like projector, smart board, and desktop and virtual online learning. Blended learning is the mixture of conventional classroom and online learning where learners and teachers are physically present. Blended mode of education is very effective approach in teaching learning process where students and teacher learn together with a lot of traditional and electronic instruments such as projector, smart board, laptop, desktop, mobile phone, tablets etc. blended learning

environment give great opportunity to the student in teaching learning process for enhancing the capability, potentials, interest, aptitude and teaching learning strategies.

- 1) Blended learning is a teaching and learning approach in which students learn through electronic or virtual media as well as formal face-to-face teaching and learning in the classroom.
- 2) Blended learning is an approach of learning that integrates traditional face-to-face teaching methods with online learning activities. In an ideal world, each (both online and offline) will counterbalance the other by using its actual strength.
- 3) Blended learning is a strategy that focuses on improving students' achievement, potential, capability, and interest in the teaching learning environment, as well as optimizing learning objectives by disseminating them via personal learning technology at the appropriate time and place.
- 4) The traditional classroom approach is totally teacher-centric approach, a top-down, teacher-directed approach, but blended learning is a student-centric and bottom-up approach.
- 5) Blended learning provides learning that is effective, interesting, and more effective as compared to the traditional approach.
- 6) Blended learning gives flexibility to the students as well as the teacher, it engages the students for a long time.
- 7) In a blended learning environment, students actively participate and achieve self-learning, self-engagement, research skills, creativity, better decision-making, self-responsibility, etc.

The most significant and crucial element of the Y2K educational methodology for a holistic learning approach, blended learning, is not only one of the most varied and diversified segments in the current educational system but also one of the most dormant. Blended learning increase the quality and capability of valuable teaching learning experience. As a result of the paradigm shift in higher education, which takes into account globalization, rapid technological advancement, the 3D formula of the current education system (digitization, digitalization, and digital transformation), as well as the need to improve the quality of current education, institutions are now planning their policies to incorporate new modes and methods of teaching. As a result of blended learning, students' interest and motivation capability increases significantly, which breaks up the routine of the classroom with video recorded lectures, live video, and other digitally enabled learning opportunities.

Related Literature Review

Buket et al. (2008) a study on learners styles of learning and their views on blended learning. 34 students were selected of Ankara university of Turkey. Found that students views on blended learning such as usage of technology, environment, evaluation face to face environment, infrastructure of information communication technology are differ to their learning styles. Result of the study shows that no significant difference between students' level of academic achievements and their learning styles. Wang et al. (2015) aims of the study to bridge gap in blended learning research and what is the requirement for achieving in blended learning. 87 empirical studies were included in this research for the literature and gaps of the research. There is a several gap and practice are found in blended learning. For the achieving of blended learning approach we have required best infrastructure and trained teacher. Anthony et al. (2022) Blended learning adaptation and implementation in higher education. In this study the researcher found that innovative learning techniques and rapidly modification in teaching learning process and further found through systematic review hoe the blended learning implemented and adopted and what is the requirement for the blended learning classroom according to the researcher a systematically analyzing the reviews and meta-analysis of 94 studies that is from 2004 to 2020 found that the factors those are influence on students, teachers and administrators for adopting blended learning environment at higher education level. For the adaptation of blended learning infrastructure is more important, and the cooperation of school management committee or higher authority should be required. Result of the study reveals that learners, teacher and administration role is very essential for the implementation of blended learning environment at higher education level. Mushtaq and Banwaree Lal (2022) Blended Mode of education and its relevance in teaching learning process. Blended learning is more effective, interesting and motivated for the students as well as teachers and enhance the learning potentials, improve the better relation between teacher and students and give freedom to the students. And further found that blended learning required well infrastructure, good experts in ICT, good teacher student's relationship, better networking system for effective and interesting teaching learning process. If we have best resources in information communication technology the teaching process will be skilful and reached at higher standard and students will gain more and more knowledge.

Research Question

What is the role of blended learning for holistic education in 21st century?

Methodology

In order to identify the role of blended learning for holistic education in 21st century, the researchers have secondary source of data and adopted qualitative and analytical approach for the study.

Role of Blended Learning for Holistic Education in 21st Century

Blended learning plays an important role in educational landscape. It increase the students involvement for long time, enhanced teacher students relationship, improve students learning strategies, interest, motivation, achievement and potentials, provides flexibility for self-responsible, self-engagement and decision making, give opportunity for time management, experimental learning, creativity, intellectual thinking, logical reasoning and brainstorming etc. Blended learning plays a major role in teaching learning environment such as'

- 1) Blended learning increase the student's interest for focusing on content matter.
- 2) Keep students focused for long time, increases the students engagements and interactions towards the learning.
- 3) Blended learning provides freedom to the students as well as teacher.
- 4) It provide autonomy to the students for self-driven and responsible tracking their assignment for assessment and evaluations.
- 5) Blended learning is a student centric approach it gives opportunity to students ownership.
- 6) Blended learning enables students for diagnostic information and student's feedback.
- 7) It provides opportunity to the students for acquiring knowledge at their own pace, through the access of internet, web sites and social Media's platform etc.
- 8) BL gives students a better chance to study together.
- 9) BL offers intellectual and expert efforts as instruction.
- 10) More flexibility in the teaching and learning process.
- 11) Students can access their course materials outside of the classroom at home using an online portal.
- 12) BL improve learning across the curriculum, co-curriculum, and other sorts of learning activities, in addition to the particular subject.
- 13) To enhance digital learning abilities.
- 14) Blended teaching and learning methods offer the opportunity to create resources that are open educational resources, authentic, reliable and valid.
- 15) The blended learning approach is not one way methods of teaching, it is students centric as well as teacher-centered also.
- 16) In blended learning teacher works as a facilitator, knowledge provider, counsellor, coach and mentor.
- 17) Role of teacher in blended learning as a supportive and team leader in teaching learning process.
- 18) Blended learning prepares students for future in multi skills, research skills and better decision making, good leadership, sense of responsibility and digital literacy, digital teaching learning process.

Analysis of literature reveals that blended learning is a mere mix of traditional classroom as well as online education. Significant role of blended learning for holistic education in 21st century are found. It increase the curiosity, motivation, aptitudes, attitudes and learning strategies among students as well a teacher. Blended Learning provide the interaction between teacher and students, techniques-based learning, practical learning, motivation, encouragements, sympathy and guidance for improving the teaching learning process. Around the world where emergence of education and technology are increasingly day by day. Particularly attention will need to pay on emerging technology that will transform the education system. Blended learning enables students to access online platform such as, open education resource, internet, presentation, research journal, publication encyclopedia, e-dictionaries etc. In 21st century blended learning integrate some tools that are effective in teaching learning process such as; Inklewriter, Powtoon, Tagxedo Wordle, Google doc, Google slides, Eterpads, ScatterSpoke, Idea boardz, Open Educational Resource, Online Assessment and Portfolio, Smart classroom, Electronic Devices and some software application are Google meet, Google classroom, Zoom, WebEx, Study Blue Flashcards, Schoology, Quiz, Teacher Kit, Animoto, Socrative, Seesaw, Tether, FoxFi, Too Noisy, Answer Garden, Slido, websites etc.

Conclusion

Following the COVID pandemic, the university grant commission advised institutions to teach 40% of the curriculum online and 60% offline. The main purpose of National Education Policy 2020 is to provide high-quality education in order to change India into a more dynamic, energetic, educated society and a global knowledge superpower by making education at all levels, especially at the school and college level, more holistic, flexible, multidisciplinary, and powerful for the students. At present, blended modes of education play an important role in transforming the teaching and learning process in the form of holistic education. Education through blended learning is very effective and successful for students and teachers alike. Findings of the study showed that face-to-face teaching with the use of technology such as projectors, smart boards, laptops, desktop computers, and some software applications makes learning effective and enhances learner and teacher competences, curiosity, inspiration, enthusiasm, and learning potential as well as problem-solving abilities, creativity, logical reasoning, intellectual thinking, cognitive ability, etc. The conclusion of the study shows that blended learning plays a major role in the development of education in the 21st century. Blended education provides a better opportunity for enhancing the student's overall performance with their teaching and learning process. Moreover, we have required better infrastructure for blended learning and the best-trained teachers for holistic education. If we have a good budget and a better management system with 21st century skills for the betterment of blended learning environments, then the standard of education will be reached at a higher level.

References

- [1] Akkoyunlu, B., & Soylu, M. Y. (2008). A Study of Student's Perceptions in a Blended Learning Environment Based on Different Learning Styles. *Educational Technology & Society*, 11 (1), 183-193.
- [2] Anthony, B., Kamaludin, A., Romli, A. (2022). Blended Learning Adoption and Implementation in Higher Education: A Theoretical and Systematic Review. *Tech Know Learn* 27, 531–578. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-020-09477-z>
- [3] Mushtaq, M., & Meena B., L. (2022) Blended Mode of education and its relevance in teaching learning process. *Post Covid Education Scenario in India*. G.H.G. Khalsa Colleges, Gurusar Sadhar Twenty first century publications Patiala. 73-78.
- [4] NEP (2020). New Education Policy. Ministry of Human Resource Development Government of India. Retrieved from www.education.in
- [5] University Grant Commission New Delhi. Blended Mode of Teaching and Learning: A Concept Note.
- [6] Vallee, A., Blacher, J., Cariou, A., and Sorbets, E.,(2022) Blended Learning Compared to Traditional Learning in Medical Education: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. 22(8)16504 doi: 10.2196/16504
- [7] Wang, Y., Han, X., & Yang, J. (2015). Revisiting the Blended Learning Literature: Using a Complex Adaptive Systems Framework. *Educational Technology & Society*, 18 (2), 380–393.

GENDER AND EDUCATION

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Introduction

Gender can be described as a social construct that refers to the roles, behaviours, and deities that a society considers appropriate for men and women. Gender is not the same as sex, which refers to the biological and physiological characteristics that define males and females. Gender shapes the way individuals experience and interact with the world, including their experiences in education. In this topic, we can explore the ways in which gender affects educational opportunities, outcomes, and experiences for both men and women. We can also examine the ways in which educational institutions and society perpetuate or challenge gender inequality and stereotyping. This discussion will provide insight into the complex and nuanced ways in which gender shapes education and the potential for creating more equitable and inclusive education systems. Education can be defined as the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits through various means such as training, research, or self-study. Education is important for mankind because it provides individuals with the tools and skills necessary to navigate the world and make informed decisions. Education also plays a critical role in development and is linked to economic growth and social mobility. The importance of education for girls is particularly significant as girls and women have historically been denied equal education opportunities. Education empowers girls to make informed decisions about their lives, including their health, relationships, and career choices. Educated girls are also more likely to delay marriage and childbirth, have smaller families, and have better economic prospects. Furthermore, educating girls has a ripple effect because it leads to better health and education outcomes for their communities. However, these gender differences are not always consistent across cultures or socio-economic groups. Additionally, there are disparities in access to education for girls and women in many parts of the world, which can contribute to inequality in educational attainment and workforce participation. Furthermore, societal gender stereotypes can influence the educational choices and career aspirations of both boys and girls, which can limit their potential.

Gender Inequality

Gender inequality refers to the unequal treatment or perceptions of individuals based on their gender. This can take many forms, including discrimination in the workplace, unequal pay, a lack of representation in leadership positions, and social biases and stereotypes. Gender inequality is a persistent problem in many societies around the world, and efforts to address it include legislation, cultural change, and individual action to challenge sexist stereotypes and promote equality.

Gender Discrimination in Education

Even in this century, we can find gender discrimination in many parts of the world. While girls have made significant progress in terms of access to education in recent years, they continue to face many barriers to achieving educational success. Some examples of gender discrimination in education include

- 1) Unequal access to education – In some countries girls faces barriers to attend school such as poverty, early marriage and cultural norms that prioritize boys' education over girls.
- 2) Unequal educational opportunities – Even when girls are able to attend school, they may not have access for the same quality of education or opportunities as boys. For example-girls may be more likely to attend schools that are in poor condition or have fewer resources.
- 3) Gender based violence and harassment – Girls may face harassment and violence on their way to school or while in school which can discourage them from attending or negatively impact their educational performance.
- 4) Gender bias and stereotypes – Teachers and other education professionals may hold unconscious biases that lead them to expect less of girls and discourage them from pursuing certain subjects or careers.
- 5) Unequal distribution in STEM education. Girls and young women are underrepresented in fields such as engineering, computer science and physics.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach, including policies and programs to increase girls' access to education, efforts to create a safe and inclusive learning environment, and targeted initiatives to promote girls' participation in fields such as STEM education.

Girls Suffering in Education Because of Gender Discrimination

Girls are suffering in education as a result of gender discrimination in a variety of ways, including lower enrolment and attendance rates as a result of cultural norms, poverty, and other barriers.

Poor Educational Outcomes

Girls may not perform as well academically as boys due to a lack of resources, discrimination from teachers or peers, or other factors.

Limited Educational and Career Opportunities

Girls may be steered away from certain subjects or career paths due to stereotypes and biases about what is appropriate for girls to study or pursue.

Lower Economic and Social Mobility

Without access to education, girls and women may be less likely to secure well-paying jobs, which can trap them in poverty and limit their ability to improve their lives and the lives of their families.

How Gender Inequality Affects the Literacy of Women in Various Countries

Girls who do not have access to education can suffer in a variety of ways, including lower economic and social mobility, poor health outcomes, and limited opportunities for personal and professional development. In Afghanistan, only 12% of girls attend secondary school, and many girls are forced into marriage at a young age, which can limit their ability to access education and other opportunities. A UNICEF report found that girls who do not attend school are more likely to be married as children, have larger families, and be more likely to die during pregnancy or childbirth. In Sub-Saharan Africa, many girls face barriers to attending school due to factors such as poverty, cultural norms, and the burden of domestic responsibilities. A World Bank report found that in countries like Burkina Faso, Faro, Chaal, and Mali, girls are up to three times more likely to be out of school than boys. In Pakistan, girls face significant barriers to accessing education, including cultural norms, poverty, and a lack of infrastructure. A report from the Human Rights Commission of Pakistan found that only 22% of girls in Pakistan attend secondary school and that girls are more likely to be out of school in rural and conflict-affected areas.

Impact of Gender Inequality on Men

Gender inequality in education affects men as well. Although the effects may be different from those experienced by women, Men may be discouraged from pursuing careers in fields such as teaching or nursing that are traditionally considered to be "female" fields. Men may also feel pressure to conform to societal expectations that they should be the primary breadwinners for their families, and this may discourage them from pursuing education or career opportunities that may pay less but have more fulfilment. Men may also face limited participation in education related to caregiving as it is often seen as a feminine role. This can limit their ability to provide care for children, the elderly, or disabled family members. Men may also face limited access to mental health support in education and in general, as the societal expectation that men should be strong and not show emotions can discourage men from seeking help.

Factors that Affect Transgender in Education

Transgender individuals face a unique challenge in accessing education due to discrimination and stigma related to their gender identity. They may face harassment and discrimination from peers, teachers, and staff, which makes them feel unsafe and uncomfortable. This may lead to poor academic performance, absenteeism, and even dropouts. Schools may lack policies and practices that support transgender students, such as policies on name and pronoun use, access to bathrooms, and the ability to participate in sports. Transgender students may have committed access to resources such as counselling, health care, and extracurricular activities, which can negatively impact their educational experience. Transgender students may also face limited access to mental health support in school and in general due to society's lack of understanding and acceptance of transgender people.

International Girl's Child's Day

The UN established International Girl Child's Day in 2012 to recognize the rights and unique challenges faced by girls around the world, which is to be observed on October 11th to promote girls' empowerment and the fulfilment of their human rights. The theme changes every year, such as Empowering Adolescent Girls, Ending the Cycle of Violence, Girl Force Unscripted and Unstoppable.

National Girl's Child's Day

Similar to International Girl Child Day, the Ministry of Women and Child Development of our Indian Government started observing National Girl Child Day in 2008 every year on January 24th to raise awareness about the rights of the girl child and the challenges they face. The ministry focused on the importance of educating and empowering the girl child. The government launched various schemes, programs, and initiatives to promote the welfare of girl children in the country. NGO civil society organizations, schools, and colleges celebrate this day by conducting various programs like debates, discussions, rallies, and cultural events to spread awareness about the rights and needs of the girl child. The National Girl Child Day serves as a reminder of the importance of investing in the education, health, and well-being of girls and young women, which is critical for constructing a more equitable and just society.

Organizations that Work for Gender Equality

Un Woman: This is a United Nations agency that works to promote gender equality and the empowerment of women. They work to end discrimination against women, promote women's rights, and empower women to participate fully in all aspects of life. Girl Rising: This is a global organization that works to change the way the world values girls through education. They use storytelling partnerships and campaigns to change the way girls are perceived, valued, and treated and to empower girls to reach their full potential. Plan International: This is an organization that works to promote child rights and gender equality. They work to ensure that girls have access to education. Health care and protection from violence and exploitation. Malala Fund: This is an organization founded by Malala Yousufzai a young girl from Pakistan who was shot by the Taliban for advocating for girl's education. The organization works to empower girls through education by supporting community led programmes, investing in girls' education leaders and advocacy efforts. Educate Girls: This is an organization that works to promote literacy and gender equality in education. They work to provide girls with access to education and to empower girls through literacy programs and mentoring. UNESCO: UNESCO monitors and reports enrolment, dropout, and literacy rates, as well as supports policy development and advocacy efforts. It also provides technical assistance and supports member states in developing and implementing policies that promote gender equality in education. such as scholarships for girls, teacher training programs, and programs to promote girls' participation in STEM education. UNESCO provides educators, policymakers, and other state holders with training and capacity building to help them better understand gender issues and support their efforts to promote gender equality in education. UNESCO also collaborates with other organizations, including non-governmental organizations, to promote the same; for example, UNESCO runs joint programs with GEM (Global Education Monitoring Report), GEFI (Global Education First Initiative), EFA (Education for All), and UNICEF. It also works with sustainable development goals (SDG) to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. UNESCO has launched several campaigns to promote gender equality, such as EFA (Education for all), Girls Education, Gender Main streaming in education, Global Education Monitoring, Global education first initiative (GEFI), For promoting gender equality in education.

Conclusion

The implicit promise that gender relations will change and empower women thanks to girls' equal involvement in education does not seem to be true in these areas. Whether and how schooling does and might play a transformative role in people's individual lives and in promoting gender equity is significantly impacted by the complexity of educational practices, labor and marriage markets, family survival strategies, and gendered family, community, and school relations. The goal of universal education must be adopted by society as a movement. The example of India demonstrates that advantages have been both quicker and more evenly distributed wherever education has been a social norm.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

SPORTS ENRICH BETTER LIFE STYLE

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Abstract

In recent decades, sport as a social practice has become relevant in many different fields: in health, life style, economy, politics, education, work and leisure. The importance of sport transcends the confines of the sports field. Sport is about organizing collective efforts and performance. Sport is about managing excellence, coaching and developing tactics as well as strategies. Sport also has its own mechanisms of organizing social differences. The competitive aspects of sport imply practices of in- and exclusion. These practices are enacted spatially on the sports field, dividing space between competing teams and individual sportsmen and sportswomen. In a broader sense, this theme touches upon the issue of access and socially marginalized identities. Sport deals with contradictions and paradoxes that exist in society at large. Sport is an arena in which social and political differences are being played out. Over all the sports enrich the better life style.

Keywords: *Sports And Life Style*

Introduction

Sport pertains to any form of competitive physical activity or game that aims to use, maintain, or improve physical ability and skills while providing enjoyment to participants and, in some cases, entertainment to spectators.

Sports Teaches Values

Fairness, Team Building, Equality, Discipline, Inclusion, Perseverance, and Respect

Sports Boost Your Self Confidence

The regular exercise that comes with playing sports can boost your confidence and improve your self-esteem

Sports Build Leadership Traits

Team sports such as soccer, baseball, and basketball are breeding grounds for leadership traits.

Sports Improve Concentration

Regular physical activity helps keep your key mental skills sharp as you age.

Sports Reduce Stress and Depression

When you are physically active, your mind is distracted from daily stressors. This can help you avoid getting bogged down by negative thoughts. Exercise reduces the levels of stress hormones in your body.

Sports Improves Health & Protection Against Disease

The Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recommend sports participation as a healthy way to maintain weight.

Conclusion

By these we can conclude that by the sports it can enrich the better life style for the human beings to have healthy and happy life .Sports can develop us the over nature and character of the persons.

Reference

- [1] Anderssen, N., and Wold, B. (1992). Parental and peer influences on leisure-time physical activity in young adolescents. *Res. Quart. Exer. Sport* 63, 341–348. doi: 10.1080/02701367.1992.10608754
- [2] Archambault, I., Eccles, J. S., and Vida, M. N. (2010). Ability self-concepts and subjective value in literacy: joint trajectories from grades 1 through 12. *J. Educ. Psychol.* 102, 804–816.

MULTICULTURALISM IN INDIA - THE PRESENT CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Multiculturalism is an amalgamation of different races, nationalities, languages, religions, classes, gender, etc. It's a view that people from different cultures have equal rights. It's geared toward assuming a common political culture that all can participate in. It supports cultural coexistence. Multiculturalism is a philosophy of evidence, acceptance of Different culture under a same jurisdiction. India is a land of diversity. It is a blend of multi religious and ethnic group. Every state has not only their language but they have their different food habits, dress code, religion, culture etc. The cultural diversity of India has been saved by its long history it's geography and diverse demography. India has historically been a multicultural society. North-East is one of the most Culturally diverse areas of the world. It is the home to about 200 tribes. The term unity in diversity fits perfectly with the regional landscape. Since every linguistic community irrespective of their size and population in northeast nurture idiosyncrasies their cultures. This Article is an effort to look at the multiculturalism in Indian society, ethnic groups' and its contemporary challenges.

Introduction

The term Multiculturalism is one of the important contemporary concepts to political science. Multiculturalism is closely related to culture. By culture we mean the shared ways of life, shared beliefs, ways of thinking an understanding of the world around us in which we situate others and ourselves on different grounds. Culture is one of the unique characteristics of human society. Every society has its own culture. But in this present day society, it is also seen that a society consists of people belonging to different cultures. The existence of different cultures in a society has led to the rise of multiculturalism. It tries to restore a sense of wholeness in a post modern era that fragments human life and thought. It encourages the minority communities to participate fully in society by enhancing their level of economic, social and cultural integration into the host culture. As a descriptive term multiculturalism has been taken to refer to cultural diversity. As a normative term it implies a positive endorsement even elaboration of communal diversity typically based on respect and recognition to different groups.

Multiculturalism as a Concept

The concept 'Multiculturalism' in its literal sense means "multiplicity of cultures". It is the concept that several different cultures can coexist peacefully and equitably in a single country. In a society or country, we find people of different religions, languages, races and cultures. They have their different religious beliefs, speak different languages and they have different cultures. Multiculturalism recognizes and affirms this plurality and diversity of cultures, traditions, religions and so on. It attaches equal respect to these different cultural diversities of the society. The term 'multiculturalism' has been first used by the Swiss in 1957 to identify their country with four spoken languages and different religions. It was again developed in the New York of USA during 1960's. In the 70's the concept reached in Australia and Canada who officially declared themselves as multicultural states. Then after it had reached to Western Europe. But as a whole the concept of multiculturalism got its first legal implementation through the Canadian Multiculturalism Act of 1988.

The main characteristic features of multiculturalism are as under:

- 1) Multiculturalism believes on Multiplicity of cultures.
- 2) It is a concept that denotes that several different cultures can co-exist peacefully and equitably in a single country.
- 3) It recognises and accepts all cultures of the society as equal .
- 4) A multicultural society grants equitable status to distinct cultural and religious groups.
- 5) It gives equal respect to all kinds of people in a society.
- 6) Multiculturalism helps people to acquire a sense of tolerance and peace towards other cultures.
- 7) It also helps us to connect with people of other cultures and know how to co-operate with them.

Multiculturalism and Democracy

The issue of ethnicity group identity, and cultural plurality with states or politics is one of the significant issues in contemporary politics. More specifically multi-ethnic and linguistic or cultural differences are the contemporary problems which has posed a threat to democratic norms and rules. These differences grow stronger and sometimes differences become the very substances of political strife. As a result of the changing contemporary social system of the state the cultural differences have become a source of various political and social clashes. For various reasons the multi-ethnic and cultural communities have moved towards socio-political movements. In fact, the most important reasons for these movements is their identity crisis. As a result various ethnic movements organised by the multi ethnic minority people have to be seen. These movements have posed and are posing a serious threat to the democratic governments of contemporary states. Multiculturalism denotes that all cultures should give equal respect and recognition. Here we can take an example of granting turban wearing Sikh people in Canada. Legally in that country , the government declared that wearing of helmet by both motorcycle drivers and passengers was compulsory. But the Sikh people living in Canada demanded that they couldn't use helmet at the time of driving and the Canadian Govt accepted their demand only for the respect of their traditional cultures.

Besides, the Indian constitution also has given cultural rights to every cultural communities of India. In Article 29, the constitution lays down that "any section of the citizens residing in the territory of India or any part thereof having a distinct language script or cultures of its own shall have the right to conserve the same." In contemporary times, it is seen that liberal democracy (especially the democracy of the third worlds) has been facing a problem and that is the politicization of culture. Various political parties have made culture as their political issue for winning elections. They even don't hesitate to create cultural clashes among various multicultural communities. Again as have already said that many ethnic movements have arisen as a result of cultural differences among the people. So, in such a situation multiculturalism can play a vital role because it gives equal status and recognition to these diverse cultures. Here, we can say that the governments of various liberal democratic countries have become successful to some extent, to give equal rights to these multi-ethnic and cultural communities. For example, modern democratic states have granted various freedom to these communities like freedom to move independently, rights to form organizations, freedom of speech and expressions and so on. But the Govt should do more for these communities and then only the fruits of democracy will be eaten by all without any discrimination and real democracy will be established.

Multiculturalism in India

India is the most wonderful country after Africa in respect of language, caste, religion, culture and ethnicity. The practice of multiculturalism in India is quite different to that of America and other Western countries. The difference is here that where as the Western developed countries have to adopt their multicultural policy for giving justice to the foreigners or internally migrated cultural minority communities but the Indian cultural diversity is the natural or hereditary cultural diversity. Indian society is based on the concept of "unity amidst diversity". In its long history India has received many people from all over the world . They came here as traders migrants, invaders travellers and began to be settled here permanently. So, even though India has a vast array of people each with its own food habits, languages, dresses, religions, castes and regions they live here as a part of a single civic culture. Now, India has more than 1800 languages (among them over 400 are spoken languages) and over a hundred different communities based on language religion and caste so, multiculturalism is present in Indian society. The country has been a home to foreigners for many centuries. It had been invaded by the Muslim forces as early as the 7th century A.D. Besides the European settlers landed in Kollam Kerala as early as the 16th Century. According to 2008 census the total Hindu population is 80.5%, Islam 13.4%, Christianity 2.3% and Sikhs accounted for 19%. Thus we see that the diversity of religious belief system existing in India today. The assimilation and social integration of religions brought to the region by traders, travellers, migrants and even invaders and conquerors. Here, a debate arises whether this multicultural system is advantageous or not in Indian society. India has had her fair share of communal indifferences with innumerable riots and violences. Perhaps the most infamous being the 'Godhra incident of 2002 & Babri Masjid case'. The Godhra incident broke out by the Godhra burning and resulting communal violence between Hindus and Muslims on 27 February 2002 at Godhra city of Gujarat state. At that day a train named Sabarmati Express was forcibly stopped and attacked by a large muslim mob. As a result, 58 Hindu pilgrims including women and children were burnt alive. This attack prompted retaliatory massacres against Muslims on a large scale. Again, we can take the example of Shiv Sena - a regional political party of Maharashtra. It is a far right political party which was founded by Bal Thackeray on 19th June, 1966. This party favoured an increase in influence and power of Maharashtrian people in Maharashtra.

It propagated the agenda that Maharashtra belonged to the Maharashtrians and thus they should be given preference over immigrant or outsiders. For this purpose, this party often resorts to violence against people belonging to other communities. Its followers have gone so far as to burn cricket pitch where an Indo-pak cricket match was scheduled to be held. Another communal violence which India faced is Babri Masjid case. During the 16th century, the chief commander of the Mughal Emperor Babar built a mosque in Ayodhya of UP. It is said that before building mosque there was a temple of Lord Rama and the mosque was built by demolishing the temple. As a result, a clash started between the Hindus and Muslims since that time. After independence of India this issue became political issue. In Feb 1980, the Faizabad district court ordered that the Babri Masjid premises be unlocked so that Hindus could pray at the site which they considered as the birth place of Lord Rama. In Dec 1992 the supporting organizations of the construction of Ram Mandir had organised a Karseva. For that purpose lacs of people reached Ayodhya and a tense situation arose on Dec 6 of the same year. The demolition of Babri Masjid again showed the failure of secularism & multiculturalism. Thus we see that the advantages of multicultural society are not present currently in the Indian society. As of now, the horrors of communalities and religious differences have torn a part a country rich in culture & heritage. But it can be said that with the advent of modern education and globalization of the younger generations we could move towards a utopian world where cultural differences would not exist.

The Challenges of Multiculturalism in India

The early 1970s marked the beginning of multicultural movement first in Canada and Australia then in USA , UK ,Germany and elsewhere. India has historically been a multicultural society. India has about 1,632 different languages and dialects. There are 22 official languages in the Indian Constitution and 2011 census report declares that about 79.80% of the population is Hindus, 14.23% Muslims, 2.3% Christians, 1.72% Sikhs, 0.7% Buddhists, 0.37% Jains and 0.66% of other religions. Society despite the fact that the Indian Constitution declares the state to be secular; religion, language and other such factors persist in the public sphere. Within the large Indian society, each culture's distinct characteristics are still recognizable just like the ingredients in a salad bowl, which contribute to the overall composition of the salad bowl. However it is indeed tragic that in the recent past, multiculturalism in India has become a battleground. A variety of societal movements were responsible for sowing the seeds of multicultural society. Various forms of identity politics immerse on the basis of religion, caste. Identity politics has created the culture of "us and them". Repeated incidents of terror attacks have widens the charms between the Hindus and Muslims.

Conclusion

India is known for unity in diversity and a thriving democracy from the past 75 years. This is because the Indian multiculturalism accepts this diversity and thus strengthened democracy by giving variety and equal status to all communities. Threat to multiculturalism Comes when a group starts thinking in a narrow way considering themselves the superior to others and show discrimination and animosity to other groups. Against this discrimination posed by multiculturalism , every Indian should uphold that unity and integrity of nation, maintain the peace and harmony, observed the fundamental duties ,respect the fundamental rights and the freedoms guaranteed under the constitution to all sections of the people. Everyone should promote the Right understandings of religions ,stress the Common Core of all religions. It is the duty of every citizen to build up the public opinions against Communalism, religious fundamentalism, religious and cultural discrimination. Today India need not just a "Culture of Democracy" but a "Democracy of Cultures." The Indian people must the right to have and to express the multiple identities of language, of region ,of religion within the framework of common citizenship .It's our duty that we must not allow " Multicultural India" to become a "Monochromatic India".

References

- [1] RegeSharmila(2003): Sociology of Gender, Sage Publications, New Delhi, Thousand Oaks London. Mallick, Md. Ayub (2013, Sept.-Oct.),
- [2] Multiculturalism, Minority Rights and Democracy in India", IOSR-Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, Vol. 16, Issue 1, 72-82.
- [3] Ali Rattansi(2011): "Multiculturalism: A Very Short Introduction", (Sage publications)
- [4] Basu.D.D(1997): Introduction to the Constitution of India. (New Delhi: Prentice-Hall of India)

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study focuses on getting an overview about Intercultural education in India, its need, its goal, its dimensions, its obstacles, its benefits and recommends for concentrated efforts by government and other institutions to get better results.

Education

Education is a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, especially the transmission of knowledge. But they often include other aims as well, such as fostering skills and character traits.

Culture

Culture refers to the social behavior, institutions, and norms found in human societies, as well as the knowledge, beliefs, arts, laws, customs, capabilities, and habits of the individuals in these groups. Culture is often originated from or attributed to a specific region or location. Humans acquire culture through the learning processes of enculturation and socialization, which is shown by the diversity of cultures across societies.

Multicultural Education

Multicultural education refers to any form of education or teaching that incorporates the histories, texts, values, beliefs, and perspectives of people from different cultural backgrounds. Multicultural education is predicated on the principle of educational equity for all students, regardless of culture, and it strives to remove barriers to educational opportunities and success for students from different cultural backgrounds.

Indian Culture

India is home to over a billion people, accommodating incredible cultural diversity between languages, geographic regions, religious traditions and social stratifications. Indians generally accept Karma, be modest and are light hearted paying the way to the beautify say "Unity in Diversity"

Need of Multicultural Education

- 1) A multicultural curriculum exposes various cultural values through activities, lectures, discussions, etc.
- 2) It allows to identify cultural as well as physical differences.
- 3) It also develops a sense of respect amongst participants.
- 4) Implementing a multicultural curriculum at a young age nurtures students to reflect on their cultural diversity with pride.
- 5) It implants patience, liberalism, and individualism in students.
- 6) It fosters friendships, encourages interaction, and improves communication skills.

Goal of Multicultural Education

Multicultural education seeks to create equal educational opportunities for all students, including those from different racial, ethnic, and social-class groups. Multicultural education tries to create equal educational opportunities for all students by changing the total school environment so that it will reflect the diverse cultures and groups within a society and within the nation's classrooms. Multicultural education is a process because its goals are ideals that teachers and administrators should constantly strive to achieve.

Challenges of Multicultural Education

Lack of cultural awareness: Lack of cultural awareness creates many difficulties in building mutual cultural tolerance among students. Without culture awareness, preservation, nurture and transition of culture will not be possible. It is necessary to develop multicultural ideology in the society along with the students, it has become difficult due to lack of multicultural awareness. Cultural conflicts: Cultural conflict is a pre-existing

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conflict. Cultural conflict creates prejudices against each other's cultures. At the same time, it seeks to dominate the minority culture over the majority culture. Therefore, cultural conflict has created a huge obstacle in multicultural curriculum and cultural education. Social inequality: Indian society is divided into different religions, castes, ethnicities, creeds, languages, genders. Therefore, it is difficult to create a sense of unity in the society. In such a situation, brotherly respect does not develop in the society. Many disadvantaged groups are aware that they are being subjected to socio-cultural and political injustice. So social inequality is an important obstacle in multicultural education. Lack of multicultural teaching strategies: If a multicultural approach is to be inculcated in the students, the multicultural teaching strategy needs to be adopted by the teacher but to a large extent the multicultural teaching work policy is not followed by the teachers. Adoption of holistic teaching methods by the teacher creates interest in the students in terms of learning but most of the teachers do not appear to be doing so, making it difficult for the multicultural approach to take place in the students.

Dimensions of Multicultural education

The five dimensions are

Content integration: Content integration deals with the extent to which teachers use examples and content from a variety of cultures and groups to illustrate key concepts, principles, generalizations, and theories in their subject area or discipline. The infusion of ethnic and cultural content into a subject area is logical and not contrived when this dimension is implemented properly. **The knowledge construction process:** The knowledge construction process describes teaching activities that help students to understand, investigate, and determine how the implicit cultural assumptions, frames of references, perspectives, and biases of researchers and textbook writers influence the ways in which knowledge is constructed. **Prejudice reduction:** The prejudice reduction dimension of multicultural education seeks to help students develop positive and democratic racial attitudes. It also helps students to understand how ethnic identity is influenced by the context of schooling and the attitudes and beliefs of dominant social groups. The theory developed by Gordon Allport (1954) has significantly influenced research and theory in intergroup relations. He hypothesized that prejudice can be reduced by interracial contact if the contact situations have these characteristics: (1) they are cooperative rather than competitive; (2) the individuals experience equal status; and (3) the contact is sanctioned by authorities such as parents, principals and teachers. **An equity pedagogy:** An equity pedagogy exists when teachers modify their teaching in ways that will facilitate the academic achievement of students from diverse racial, cultural, socioeconomic, and language groups. This includes using a variety of teaching styles and approaches that are consistent with the range of learning styles within various cultural and ethnic groups, such as being demanding but highly personalized when working with American Indian and Native Alaskan students. It also includes using cooperative learning techniques in math and science instruction to enhance the academic achievement of students of color.

Overcoming Obstacles of Intercultural Education in India

Developing awareness: Government must take strenuous efforts to spread the understanding of unique Indian culture, the need to cherish it to its population. As discussed earlier since Indians follow different cultural styles they tend to stick to Intercultural traditions and isolating themselves from customs and practices of other traditions, this paves the way for occasional intercultural conflicts. Government should take steps to bring in a sense of togetherness and train the public to respect other cultural practices. **Caste system:** Since Indians have been followed caste system for very long period of time they tend to follow some practices such as untouchability etc. This could be avoided by developing social knowledge and train them to treat every other individual with respect. **Focusing on younger population:** Training younger population is easier with improved technological facilities and government can focus on bringing programs and policies that attract young talent to pursue Intercultural education seriously and with interest and learn to live together with harmony.

Conclusion

The study identifies the uniqueness of variegated Indian culture and the challenges that has to be overcome to make multicultural education in India successful and demands for Government intervention to achieve significant results.

A GESTALT OF DEFIES IN THE MULTI-CULTURAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Everyone who is not involved in education may believe that teaching is a simple task. This is a huge mistake because the number of challenges teachers face with each new lesson is enormous, even in classrooms where teachers and students speak the same language and understand each other perfectly. For teachers, the classroom is always a challenge. Everyday life is filled with a variety of children, approaches, and new situations. Teachers should be well prepared to face any challenges that may arise in the course of their work. Working in a multicultural environment and developing multicultural skills in children during the educational process is one of the specific challenges. At first glance, it appears to be a simple task in a typical working environment. And, yes, it is only for teachers who have lived in a multicultural region and have extensive experience in multicultural classrooms. Consider how many challenges a teacher would face if his students were from different countries, held opposing religious beliefs, and came from a variety of educational backgrounds. Thousands of such multicultural classes are held every day, however, and teachers must overcome a slew of obstacles in order to achieve educational goals. The paper analyses the same, brings about the pitfalls in the teaching, provide solutions to these issues and how they can be addressed in multicultural education. The purpose of this research was to identify the challenges that teachers face in multicultural classroom settings. A phenomenology design was used in the study. Teachers from various cultures and with varying levels of professional experience participated in the study.

Keywords: *Multicultural, Classrooms, Teaching Methodology And Pitfalls.*

A Gestalt of defies in the Multi-Cultural Education in India

Culture and education are inextricably linked because the cultures of teachers and students influence educational processes in the classroom. Thus, culture encompasses everything that distinguishes one group or community within a society from another: language, values, literature, worldview, food, religion, clothing, holidays, beliefs, and behaviour that shape a specific group's lifestyle. Multicultural Education is educational method/strategies that combine the narratives, writings, qualities, convictions, and points of view of people from various social backgrounds. The main goal of incorporating it into classrooms is to allow educators to modify or add exercises that emphasise diversity and social pluralism. Race, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, class, sexual orientation, and other factors are important in multicultural education. Students can be made aware of histories, cultures, and the importance of diverse groups by adapting it in schools and colleges. Furthermore, it promotes the principles of inclusion, democracy, diversity, critical thinking, a sense of togetherness, inquiry, perspective values, and many other positive characteristics. Many people seem to believe that the goals and objectives of Multigrade or cross-cultural education are to protect the cultures of minority groups by encouraging children to think broadly and to expose them to new ideas and critical thinking. All of this helps students deduce more effectively and encourages them to have a more open outlook. As a result, students are equipped with the knowledge, values, and skills required to participate in societal changes that result in justice for otherwise marginalised and excluded ethnic groups. Students gain a thorough understanding of history, culture, and society, preparing them for a diverse college classroom and a culturally diverse global market. Teachers who advocate for intercultural competence eschew textbooks that primarily focus on white Anglo-Saxon identity and instead choose teaching materials and teaching aids that cover a broader variety of cultures and historical backgrounds. This comprehensive approach results in students and employees who really are knowledgeable, inclusive, community-oriented, and empathetic. The main distinction between multicultural and regular classrooms is a language problem. Children from various countries and even cities may use the same language but just never fully comprehend each other. This could be as a result of parents, environment, dialects, and so on. As a result, students may not know how to act when the teacher is speaking, may not understand group or pair work, and may not understand the rules of newly introduced games. Another significant factor is the preponderance of visual educational resources. Because students struggle to comprehend the language, images can be more efficient in acquiring new information.

However, situations in which students do not understand the language of instruction occur more frequently. Young people are placed in a setting where an instructor speaks a different language that they do not understand, and their task is to not only understand what the teacher says, but also to gain new knowledge - a task that is twice as difficult as in traditional classrooms. Some students may feel alienated if they do not have strong

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administrative services, an all-encompassing curriculum, and school rules that encourage and support multicultural efforts. Instead of demanding recognition for their differences in culture and opportunities to share as well as experience them, they may feel compelled to blend in – like a gigantic melting pot. Others may be offended by modifications to existing education traditions and revised education requirements designed to encourage multiculturalism. To accommodate a wider variety of historical and cultural perspectives, some educators must omit or restructure portions of their lessons. As a result, their learnings are less rigorous and more generalised. A language arts teacher, for example, may only have time to talk about one of William Shakespeare's works or one of Robert Frost's poetry during the semester in order to allow for those other works of literature by authors from China, Germany, Mexico, or France. Students may expand their knowledge base, but they will know less about specific subjects. In this case, a broad approach could harm a student who is planning to major English literature or teach high school or university English literature.

To overcome these barriers teachers must foster their relationship with students; teachers must strive to be having conversations with them outside the schoolroom and curriculum. This could include allowing students to express their joys with the class at the start of class. And first foremost, it is critical to understand all of your students' diverse cultures. It is beneficial to be aware of all the civilizations to be addressed and lessons to be planned. It is sometimes far simpler to comprehend a different language than another ethnic group's body language. If a teacher is unaware of the nonverbal behaviours common in the society from which his students come, this can lead to a variety of problems and difficulties in correct interpretation. Raised hands, eye contact, and head nods, for example, can all have completely different meanings in another country. It is the teacher's responsibility as an effective multicultural teacher to identify the students' strengths and weaknesses so that she can eliminate them. Users could argue that every teacher in the classroom should present a topic from a different perspective, regardless of the students' nationality. Of course, this would be ideal, but a limited number of school lessons does not always allow for this.

The situation differs in multicultural classes. It is especially relevant in history lessons because different populations define certain events differently. Some movements, for example, should be labelled as both an expansion of one country and a displacement of another. A teacher must exercise extreme caution in his formulations and expressions so as not to offend the feelings of some students. Furthermore, he should avoid attempting to persuade others of the unquestionable truth of his words and views, as this may result in a misunderstanding. Every teacher should recognize how a person feels in an unfamiliar environment, and communication with the student's parents can help with this. It is essential to comprehend how a child was raised from early life, what customs influenced his worldview, and what is completely unacceptable to him. This information will assist teachers build more effective lessons and students find one's place within the classroom. Aside from problems in using a foreign language, students may feel shy or be unable to express themselves due to the fear of not being understood. Cultural beliefs are deeply embedded but unspoken, and people are frequently unaware of their own cultural rules until they are broken. Teachers can easily break rules that their students are unable to articulate, or they may unknowingly demand that the students break them themselves, resulting in a highly uncomfortable situation for the student. Many people wonder why multicultural education is important, but there are numerous reasons why it should be implemented in modern schools. Today, borders between countries are becoming less visible as more states welcome citizens from other nations on their territory. As a result, when a child enters a new classroom, this experience appears to be very beneficial to both him and his fellow students. The latter learn to be tolerant, patient, and open to new information, whereas a child learns to survive in an entirely new environment, and this experience is extremely valuable.

References

- [1] Adams, J.Q., J.F. Niss, and C. Suarez, eds. *Multicultural Education: Strategies for Implementation in Colleges and Universities*. Vol. 1. Macomb, IL: Western Illinois University, 1991.
- [2] Richard-Amato, P. A., & Snow, M. A. *The multicultural classroom: Readings for content-area teachers*. White Plains, NY: Longman, 1992.
- [3] Sleeter, C.E., ed. *Empowerment through Multicultural Education*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1991.
- [4] Takaki, Ronald. *A Different Mirror: A History of Multicultural America*. NY: Little, Brown and Co., 1993.

IMPACT OF COMPUTER AIDED INSTRUCTION ON DIVISION IN IMPROVING THE “PROBLEM-SOLVING EFFICIENCY” OF CHILDREN WITH LEARNING DISABILITY

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Introduction

There has been rising interest among researchers towards learning disability(LD) in worldwide due do the increasing number of LD especially in South Asia . The estimate for current learning disabilities among children of ages 3–17 years in 2007 was 7.8 percent, with 3.7 percent rated as mild and 4.0 percent rated as moderate or severe (NSCH, 2007a). The estimate for learning disabilities in 2011–2012 was 8.0 percent for children of ages 3–17, with 4 percent rated as mild and 4 percent rated as moderate or severe (NSCH, 2012). The incidence of dyslexia in Indian primary schoolchildren has been reported to be 2%–18%, dysgraphia 14%, and dyscalculia 5.5%. India is thought to have approximately 90 million people with varying degrees of learning disabilities (LDs) and an average class in school has about five students with LDs. A recent news article in Times of India states that dyslexia is the most common LD with nearly 35 million children suffering from it. (Goel2021) Kurian and James (2018) investigated the learning disability in India methodically and found 10per cent of children in India have Learning Disabilities.

Learning disabilities used to describe the seemingly unexplained difficulty a person of at least average intelligence has in acquiring basic academic skills (Lerner, 2002) specially with reference to reading, writing, language and in arithmetic skills. The other common terms used to refer this learning disability are Specific Learning Disability, Learning Difference, Learning Disorder and Learning Difficulty. Specific learning disability (SLD) comprises a heterogeneous group of disorders with the main impairment being cognitive processing. SLD is a neurodevelopmental disorder of biological origin and occurs in the absence of intellectual disability, neurological dysfunction or environmental deprivation. (Muthusamy and Sahu.2020) This leads to challenges in academic performance and has psychosocial implications, results in poor self-esteem and decreased self-confidence, disinterest towards academic work, unexpected social behaviour, increased school dropouts’ rate. Generally, children with learning disability are average or of above average in intelligence, Hence it is highly recommended that the proponents in the field of education can bring a radical change for children with this invisible disability to construct a new strategy of teaching to improve their learning efficiency. The computer aided teaching has brought a contemporary change in the field of education and gained its momentum due to its high influence, resulted in positive effects on Children with Learning Disability (LD) Foster, Anthony, Clements, Sarama, and Williams (2016) assessed the impact of using mathematics software programme for teaching maths for children who face difficulties in Math learning. From the low-income communities, nearly 37 classrooms of 9 schools were selected for the study. For the purpose of conducting the test, classrooms were equipped to receive computer-aided instruction for learning maths for 21 weeks randomly. Building Blocks software suite was used for the study and found that students who have received computer-aided instruction have scored high in posttests of applied problems and numeracy. The results indicate the effectiveness of using computer-aided teaching for children to improve their performance in mathematics. Keeping in view of this, a research study was conducted on "Impact of Computer Aided Instruction Module on Teaching Division Concept for Children With Learning Disability with the sole objective to analyse the efficacy of Computer Aided Teaching (CAT) for enhancing math concept learning in children with LD with the specific objectives as follows.

- 1) To develop, validate and implement the module on division in Maths to teach children.
- 2) ToAssess the Pre and post test scores on division .
- 3) To analyse the impact of the developed computer aided instruction on learning – efficiency of the children.

Research Methods

The study was carried out in three types of schools namely Regular School with normal children (RS), Regular School with Learning Disability Remedial Centre (RSLDR), and Special School for Children with Learning Disability (SSLD). Quasi experimental design and pre-test - post test design was chosen for the study. The total sample size was 150 children, fifty from each category. Each category had 25 as sample for control and experimental. All the selected children’s personal and family background information was collected. Socio

Economic Scale was administered to know the socio- economic class of the selected sample. Their accessibility towards the information and communication technology was also analysed. The intelligence level was assessed by administering the Raven’s Standard Progressive Matrices Test to confirm that they are free from any other mental impairment. A Computer Aided Instruction Module on Teaching Division concept for children with Learning Disability was designed. Before venturing into actual preparation views of the teachers on teaching maths was collected and considered in designing the module. Prior to implementation a pre-test was conducted on the division. The prepared module was validated by the teachers and was implemented at various levels to the experimental groups of all the three categories. Followed by the implementation a posttest was conducted.

Variables

Estimation of Problem-Solving Efficiency of Selected Sample

The problem-solving efficiency of each individual child was calculated from the scores obtained by the individual divided by the time taken to complete the same. Given below is the formula:

$$\text{Problem Solving Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Test Score}}{\text{Time Taken}}$$

Data Analysis

After making a thorough investigation, the subsequent statistical methods were applied to examine the data for testing the hypotheses and to obtain results. Simple mean, Anova, Chi – square test and Paired t - test were used to analyse the data. Table 1 exhibits the pre -test score of the children on division. It is evident from the table that in RS, the mean score of pre-tests was high in control group of children than the experimental group. Among the level, Level 1 stood first followed by level 2 and level 3 for both control and experimental group of children. A high consistency was found in level 3 test score than level 1 and level 2 as evidenced through the value of co-efficient of variation. In the case RSLDR, mean pretest score was found high at all three levels for the control group of children than the experimental group. A high consistency in test score was found in level 2 for control group and level 3 for experimental group of children as indicated by the value of co-efficient of variation. A high mean score for Level 1 and level 2 was observed for the control group in SSLD, while it was high in level 3 for experimental group. A high level of consistency was found in level 2 for both control and experimental group as evidenced through the value of co-efficient of variation.

Table 2 shows the post test scores on division. A high mean score was observed in all three levels of test of experimental group of children in RS. A high consistency was found in level 3 for control group and level 2 for experimental group as evidenced through co-efficient of variation. In the case RSLDR, similar results were observed as in RS. A high mean value for all three tests of experimental group was found. Among the levels, the highest score was in level 3. Consistency was found in level 2 for control group and level 3 for experimental group as found in the value of co-efficient of variation. A highest mean score was found for experimental group of children in SSLD in almost all levels of the test. Consistency in test score was found in level 2 for both control and experimental group. It is followed by level 2 for control and level 3 for experimental group.

Null Hypothesis (H₀)

There is no significant variation in the test scores between pre and posttests and between the types of schools. In order to examine the null hypothesis, ANOVA test is applied and the results are given in Table 3

Since the p-value for between tests and between schools are less than the critical P-value (0.05) at 5 per cent level with (1, 2) degrees of freedom and (2, 2) degrees of freedom respectively, the formulated null

hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it may be concluded that there is a significant variation in scores between pre and posttests and between types of schools. The observed results are well supported by the findings of Lashley (2017), that Computer aided instructions significantly improves the academic performance of the students in Maths in comparison with the traditional method of teaching.

Table 4 exhibits the time taken by the children for completion of the pretests by both the control and experimental groups. In the case of children of RS, the mean value of time taken was found low for level 1 and level 2 of control group of children, whereas in level 2, the mean score was found high for control than experimental group of children. The consistency was found high in level 1 compared to level 2 and level 3 as evidenced through co-efficient of variation. In the case of RSLDR, the mean score was found high in level 1 and low in level 2 and level 3 for control group compared to experimental group. Consistency was found high in level 1 and level 3 for control group than the experimental group as indicated by co-efficient of variations. In the case of SSLD, a high mean score was observed in level 1 and level 3 for experimental group and in level 2 for control group. Consistency was high in all three levels for experimental group of children as evidenced through co-efficient of variation.

It is evident from Table 5 that for children in RS, the mean score was found high in all the three levels for control group of children than the experimental group. A high consistency was also observed in all three levels of control group as evidenced through the co-efficient variation. In the case of RSLDR, mean score was found high in all three levels for control group than experimental group. The values of co-efficient variation indicate that the consistency was found high in control group of children in the time taken for all the three levels of tests. A high mean score was found in all three levels of test for control group in SSLD compared to experimental group of children. Consistency was also found higher for control group than the experimental group as evidenced through co-efficient of variation.

Table 6 shows the problem-solving efficiency of children. A higher score in posttest was observed in all three levels compared to pretest in RS and The scores were 11, 6.5 and 13.7 for posttest and 5.4, 2.9 and 1.9 for pretest. In the case of RSLDR, a similar result as in RS was found. A similar a result as in RS was found in RSLDR. A higher score was found in posttest score than the pre –test score. In SSLD, a high posttest score was found in all three levels of the test. In all the three schools, the problem solving efficiency has improved the efficiency of the children with Learning Disability.

Null Hypothesis (HO)

There is no significant difference in problem solving efficiency of children between different type schools. In order to test the hypothesis (Ho), ANOVA test is applied and the results are given in Table 7. Since the p-value between levels (0.0147) and between schools (0.0321) are less than the critical P value (0.05) at 5 per cent level with (2, 4) and (2, 4) degrees of Freedom respectively, the formulated null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, it may be concluded that there is a variation in problem solving efficiency in test levels and in different types of schools.

Conclusion

Mutlu and Akgun (2019) reported a similar observation in the improvement of arithmetic skills of children having Mathematics Learning Disability (MLD). In addition, they have reported that, Computer Aided Instructions not only has improved the score but also the efficiency in terms of time taken to solve the problems. These findings are in accordance with that of the present study. Thus, it may be concluded that the module is very apt for implementation to Children with Learning Disability in teaching and learning division in Maths in all special schools for children with Learning Disability. It can also be used by normal schools.

References

- [1] Foster, M. E. (2012). Indicators of Mathematics Skill Acquisition in Children with Mild Intellectual Disability: Phonological Awareness, Naming Speed, and Vocabulary Knowledge. Georgia State University. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.425.6905&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [2] Goel U. Prevalence of selected learning disabilities among primary schoolchildren through primary school teachers: A descriptive survey. *Indian J Psy Nsg* [serial online] 2021 [cited 2023 Jan 27];18:23-8. <https://www.ijpn.in/text.asp?2021/18/1/23/318672>
- [3] Kuriyan, N. M., & James, J. (2018). Prevalence of Learning Disability in India: A Need for Mental Health Awareness Programme. Poster presentation. In First National Conference on Mental Health Education. Bengaluru, Karnataka: NIMHANS Publications.

A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VIRTUAL REALITY TOOLS TO ENRICH COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF FIRST-YEAR UNDERGRADUATE ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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Abstract

This paper is based on a study conducted to analyze the effectiveness of Virtual Reality tools to enhance students' communication skills. A questionnaire was used to test the level of speaking from first-year rural engineering students. A pre-test was conducted to test their communication skills. Activities were implemented as a way to attain an advanced level of performance in the post-test. From the analysis, to enhance speaking skills a few activities had been implemented. The result of this study provides that there is a significant difference between the performance of rural engineering students concerning their speaking skills. The purpose of the study was to assess to what extent virtual reality tools could serve as effective tools that could engage a better environment when compared to the traditional classroom.

Keywords: *Communication Skills, Virtual Reality, Activity-Based Teaching, Tools.*

Introduction

Technology plays a tremendous role in the lives of adolescents and teens as it is estimated that this group looks at their phones 150 times a day (Brandon, 2017). The use of technology can improve students' learning in schools and colleges. Today, innovative trends in educational technology are coming into action. They promote student-centered learning and emphasize collaboration and versatility. Though technology grows, on the other side, the majority of the population lives in rural areas, where they face various issues that impact the country's literacy rate. The Education Policy also emphasizes digital learning as an alternative to the conventional classroom method. But implementing this in rural areas faces some challenges such as financial issues, lack of infrastructure, guidance, and so on.

Problem Statement

In traditional classrooms, students are expected to retain information through listening, assimilation, and by completing individual work at a desk (Jacobs, 2010). Developing an environment that is favorable to students' learning in rural areas is a difficult proposition. Even though students know the subject they could not express their thoughts and ideas through speaking. Because of a lack of exposure and the use of technology, they could not communicate properly by sharing their ideas and opinions. In the end, they are less motivated because of their environment. Virtual Reality tools help learners to cater to a better education by enhancing the communication skills of rural engineering students.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess to what extent virtual reality tools could serve as effective tools that could engage a better environment when compared to the traditional classroom. And also to find the impact that virtual reality could have on students' performance. This could change the method of teaching and learning process which helps the learners to ease their communication skills. The role of teachers also changes and could update themselves in this technological world. Virtual reality could likely be a useful tool for all learners since it has been used in myriad fields.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives:

- 1) To find out the effectiveness of VR tools in developing the communication skill of rural engineering students.
- 2) To improve their speaking skill.
- 3) To compare the efficacy of VR tools in teaching with that of a conventional method of teaching

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- in enhancing their communication skills.
- 4) To find out the difference between the performance of the learners in the pre-test and the post-test.

Sample of the Study

The first-year rural engineering students are chosen for the study. The sample of the study consisted of twenty-five students of rural engineering students. The sample included both boys and girls. The teachers in rural engineering colleges use conventional methods and the usage of technology is less to improve their communication skills. Most of the students are from poor backgrounds and are the first graduates in their families.

Tools Used

The following tools were used for the study:

- 1) VR tools such as 360-degree videos, text, smartphones, VR boxes, and Google Cardboard were used to develop learners' speaking skills.
- 2) A questionnaire is used to test their level of speaking.

Methodology

VR tools such as 360-degree videos were used based on their syllabus and curriculum to design the activities for developing the speaking skills of rural engineering students. A pre-test was conducted to test their communication skills. Activities were implemented as a way to attain an advanced level of performance in the post-test.

Objectives

- 1) To enhance learners' ability to speak English effectively and with confidence.
- 2) To describe their opinions and observations of what they experience.

Activity 1

Name of the Activity: Delineate art

Type of the Activity: Pair work

Timings: 45 minutes

Target Learners: Engineering Students-Rural

Skills Focus: Speaking and Vocabulary

Teaching Aids: VR box, 360-degree video, mobile phone, Cardboard application

Instructions:

Step 1: The class is divided into two groups A and B. A group is paired with group B.

Step 2: A 360-degree video is shared with students and asked to watch it using Google cardboard which is given to a few groups.

Step 3: Students are asked to observe and immerse in the street and the roadside. They are asked to view it in 360 degrees.

Step 4: Vocabulary has been added in the video related to the scenario to enrich learners' lexis.

Step 5: After watching the video, students are asked to exchange their opinions with their pair.

Activity 2

Name of the Activity: See the sights

Type of the Activity: Individual

Timings: 45 minutes

Target Learners: Engineering Students-Rural

Skills Focus: Speaking and Vocabulary

Teaching Aids: VR box, 360-degree video, mobile phone, Cardboard application

Instructions:

Step 1: A 360-degree video is shared with students and asked to watch it using Google cardboard which is given to a few groups.

Step 2: Students are asked to observe and immerse in the park and other sights by viewing in 360 degrees.

Step 3: Vocabulary has been added in the video related to the scenario to enrich learners' lexis.

Step 4: After watching the video, students are asked to exchange their opinions with their friends.

Activity 3

Name of the Activity: Bike Ride

Type of the Activity: Individual

Timings: 45 minutes

Target Learners: Engineering Students-Rural

Skills Focus: Speaking and Vocabulary

Teaching Aids: VR box, 360-degree video, mobile phone, Cardboard application

Instructions:

Step 1: A 360-degree video is being shared with students and asked to watch it using Google cardboard which is given to them.

Step 2: Students are asked to experience the bike ride in a 360-degree view.

Step 3: Vocabulary has been added in the video related to the scenario to enrich learners' Lexus.

Step 4: After watching the video, students are asked to exchange their opinions and experience with their friends.

Zenith of Target Language

Letting students discuss with their pairs what they are immersed in and make use of the vocabulary shown in the video. Those vocabularies assist them to retain the words along with their meaning in their memory.

Virtual Reality's Impact on Students

Initially, when the cardboard box was distributed to learners, they were not that much excited to use the tool, but after watching the first video, learners were fully immersed in watching it. There is a difference between listening to a story and making them understand and asking them to share their ideas. But this virtual reality tool gives a real-time experience and learners speak what they have experienced. It's not enhancing their speaking alone, but also their body language and gestures. Students were able to speak effectively and with confidence. They could also enrich a few vocabularies which are shared in the video.

Analysis and Interpretation

From the analysis of the questionnaire and the activities are given, there is a significant difference between the performance of the rural engineering students concerning their speaking skills.

Sample	Level	No. of students	Mean	S.D	Mean difference	Calculated t-value	Df	Significance
Rural Engineering students	Pre-test	25	2.49	0.34	-4.04	-46.57	25	0.000*
	Post-test	25	6.89	0.75				

Performance of the rural engineering students in the Pre and Post-test. The table indicates the performance of the rural engineering students in the Pre-test and the Post-test. The mean value in the pre-test is 2.49 and it has increased in the post-test to 6.89. So, the mean difference is -4.04. The calculated t-value is -46.57. The associated p-value is 0.000 and it is significant at 0.05 level. The higher mean value in the post-test shows the performance of learners when compared to the mean value in the pre-test. Based on the feedback of the learners, it is clear that rural engineering students are more interested in learning through virtual reality tools than the conventional method of teaching. It is observed that the creativity of the learners and their confidence level are improved.

Limitations of the Study

The study has the following limitations,

- 1) The sample has been taken only from a rural engineering college and it is limited to twenty-five students.
- 2) Limited activities were given to find the performance of the learners using virtual reality tools.
- 3) The level of immersive is semi because it is cost-effective and it's not fully immersive which is expensive.
- 4) Only speaking skill has been focused on.

Conclusion

Using Virtual Reality tools in rural engineering students' classrooms increases the exposure of both the teachers and the students. It increases curiosity after using the tools and makes them concentrate more on the content. Though they made some grammatical errors while speaking, they spoke confidently and shared what they have experienced. As it increases the involvement of the students, the learning process becomes easier and more successful. Hence, rural engineering students acquire communication skills through the learning process by using Virtual Reality tools in their classrooms.

References

- [1] Brandon, J. (2017). The surprising reason millennials check their phones 150 times a day. Retrieved from <https://www.inc.com/john-brandon/science-says-this-is-the-reason-millennials-check-their-phones-150-times-per-day.html>
- [2] Carolan, Jennifer (2016). Why VR matters, especially in rural schools <https://techcrunch.com/2016/09/19/why-vr-matters-especially-in-rural-schools>
- [3] Chou, S. W., & Liu, C. H. (2005). Learning effectiveness in a web-based virtual learning environment: A learner control perspective. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 21(1), 65–76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2005.00114.x>.
- [4] Ergurel, D. (2016). 10 virtual reality apps transforming education. Retrieved from <https://haptic.al/10-virtual-reality-apps-transforming-educationdc7586badb9a#.tq29iiq69>
- [5] Goh, C. C. M., & Burns, A. (2012). *Teaching speaking: A holistic approach*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- [6] Iping Supriana Suwardi, Victor (2014). *The Use of Virtual Reality Systems for Education in Rural Areas*
- [7] Jacobs, H.H. (Ed). (2010). Power down. *Curriculum 21: Essential education for a changing world*, pp. 186-194). Alexandria, VA: ASCD
- [8] Lloyd, A., Rogerson, S., & Stead, G. (2017). *Imagining the potential for using virtual reality technologies in language learning*.
- [9] Sura, M. N. (2017, April). *Use of Technology in English Language Teaching and Learning at the University of Baghdad*.

HOLISTIC EDUCATION AND ITS PEDAGOGY-AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Holistic education encompasses a wide range of philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices. Its focus is on wholeness, and it attempts to avoid excluding any significant aspects of the human experience. It is an eclectic and inclusive movement whose main characteristic is the idea that educational experiences foster a less materialistic and a more spiritual worldview along with more dynamic and holistic views of reality. It also proposes that educational experience promote a more balanced development of – and cultivate the relationship among – the different aspects of the individual (intellectual, physical, spiritual, emotional, social and Aesthetic), as well as the relationships between the individual and other people, the individual and natural environment, the inner-self of students and external. world, emotion and reason, different discipline of knowledge and different form of knowing. holistic education is concerned with life experience, not with narrowly defined" basic skills".

Keyword: *Education, Holistic Education, Wholeness, Spirituality*

Introduction

Education is a word that includes all the vowels of the English alphabets. It also encompasses the best of knowledge delivered to willing learners. When the skillful teachers transact the knowledge to the ready students, the goal of education is achieved in real terms. In the 21st century, we need to understand one essential thing that the world is in flux. We are constantly changing and evolving, so whether the teaching community likes it or not, we, being teachers, adopt and adapt to these unprecedented changes.

To ensure that today's children become tomorrow's assets, teaching specific emotional skills are especially important. That is where SEL (Social Emotional Learning) plays a pivotal role. What is social-emotional learning? It is the process of developing self-control, self-awareness, and interpersonal skills that are very crucial for school, work, and life success. Teachers and parents both have to understand that instant gratification is the curse of the 21st century. Everybody wants instant fixes and instant solutions. Holistic Education promotes social-awareness and a sense of responsibility with self-confidence among the students. It helps the students to develop strong critical thinking abilities and makes them exceptional at problem-solving.

Holistic education is a fairly new movement, which began to take form as a recognizable field of study and practice in the mid-1980s in North America. It emerged as a response to the dominant worldview of mainstream education, often referred to the "mechanistic" or "Cartesian-Newtonian" worldview. Rather than attempting to provide a model of education, holistic education seeks to challenge the fragmented, Reductionistic assumptions of mainstream culture and education. In other words, holistic education is concerned with "underlying worldviews or paradigms in an attempt to transform the foundations of education. As Ron Miller (1992), one of the leaders of the movement, argues, Holistic education is not to be defined as a particular method or technique; it must be seen as a paradigm, a set of basic assumptions and principles that can be applied in diverse ways.

Review of Literature

Holistic education addresses the broadest development of the whole person at the cognitive and affective levels (Singh, 1996). It aims for the fullest possible human development enabling a person to become the very best or finest that they can be and develop fully 'those capacities that together make up a human being' (Forbes, 2003).

A main element of holistic education is its focus on the interconnectedness of experience and reality. Holistic education attempts to develop a pedagogy that is interconnected and dynamic and thus is in harmony with the cosmos. In contrast, much of traditional education tends to be static and fragmented, ultimately promoting alienation and suffering (Neves, 2009). Holistic education focuses on the relationship between the whole and the part and suggests that teaching and learning approaches need to be rooted in a larger vision. If techniques are isolated and unrelated they can become traditional education tends to be static and fragmented, ultimately promoting alienation and suffering (J, Miller 2006). Within this holistic perspective, the student is positioned as an active, participatory and critical learner who perceives and understands him/ dysfunctional. The holistic vision includes a sense of the whole person who is connected to his or her surrounding context and environment. (J, Miller 2004)

Another author, Scott Forbes (2003), has written that: Holistic education frequently claims that it wants

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to, 1) educate the whole child (all parts of the child), 2) educate the student as a whole (not an assemblage of parts), and 3) see the child as part of a whole (society, humanity, the environment, some spiritual whole, etc.) from which it is not meaningful to extract the student. Holistic education challenges the present approach to education and its obsessive focus on standards and testing. Holistic educators see this approach as reflecting a materialist and consumerist culture that has reduced schooling to the training of individuals to compete and consume in the global marketplace. In fact, the present thrust can be seen as abandoning any attempt to educate the whole human being. It reduces schooling to training for the workplace that can be easily assessed through standardized tests. (J. Miller 2007)

The Goal of Holistic Education

Holistic education aims at helping students be the most that they can be. Abraham Maslow referred to this as "self-actualization". Education with a holistic perspective is concerned with the development of every person's intellectual, emotional, social, physical, artistic, creative and spiritual potentials.

Basic Principles of Holistic Education

Educating for Human Development

The primary purpose of education is to nourish the inherent possibilities of human development. Schools must be places that facilitate the whole development of all learners. Learning must be the deepening of relationships to self, to family and community members, to the global community, to the planet, and to the cosmos.

Honoring Students as Individuals

Each learner is unique, inherently creative, with individual needs and abilities. This means welcoming personal differences and fostering in each student a sense of tolerance, respect, and appreciation for human diversity. Each individual is inherently creative, has unique physical, emotional, intellectual, and spiritual needs and abilities, and possesses an unlimited capacity to learn.

Holistic Education

The concept of "wholeness" should be at the core of the educational process. Wholeness implies that each academic discipline provides merely a different perspective on the rich, complex, integrated phenomenon of life. Holistic education celebrates and makes constructive use of evolving, alternate views of reality and multiple ways of knowing. It is not only the intellectual and vocational aspects of human development that need guidance and nurturance, but also the physical, social, moral, aesthetic, creative, and — in a nonsectarian sense — spiritual aspects.

New Role of Educators

Many of today's educators have become caught in the trappings of competitive professionalism: tightly controlled credentials and certification, jargon and special techniques, and a professional aloofness from the spiritual, moral and emotional issues inevitably involved in the process of human growth. Holistic educators hold, rather, that educators ought to be facilitators of learning, which is an organic, natural process and not a product that can be turned out on demand. Teachers require the autonomy to design and implement learning environments that are appropriate to the needs of their particular students.

Freedom of Choice

Students and parents should have opportunities for real choice at every stage of the learning process. Genuine education can only take place in an atmosphere of freedom. Freedom of inquiry, of expression, and of personal growth are all required. In general, students should be allowed authentic choices in their learning. They should have a significant voice in determining curriculum and disciplinary procedures, according to their ability to assume such responsibility.

Educating for a Participatory Democracy

Education should be based on democratic values and should empower all citizens to participate in meaningful ways in the life of the community and the planet. The building of a truly democratic society means far more than allowing people to vote for their leaders— it means empowering individuals to take an active part in the affairs of their community.

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Educating for Global Citizenship

Each individual is a global citizen. Education therefore, should be an appreciation for the magnificent diversity of human experience. Human experience is vastly wider than any single culture's values or ways of thinking. In the emerging global community, we are being brought into contact with diverse cultures and worldviews as never before in history. Holistic educators believe that it is time for education to nurture an appreciation for the magnificent diversity of human experience and for the lost or still uncharted potentials within all human beings.

Spirituality and Education

Holistic educators believe that all people are spiritual beings in human form who express their individuality through their talents, abilities, intuition, and intelligence. Just as the individual develops physically, emotionally, and intellectually, each person also develops spiritually.

Conclusion

Holistic education is an approach to pedagogy that can meet the needs of all types of learners, that can be a source of fulfillment and gratification for teachers, and that rears future citizens who will contribute a concern and mindfulness for others, for their communities, and for the planet. It is compatible with both global education and environmental education, which are also based on the principles of interdependence and connectedness. Based on this interdependent perspective, holistic education seeks to create a society where we live in harmony with the surrounding environment. It rejects consumerism as the dominant mode of being in modern society. Instead, it seeks an education that is rooted in the fundamental realities of nature and existence. Holistic education seeks to connect the part with the whole. We have tended in education to forget the larger vision of wholeness and connectedness, and holistic education calls on us to restore that vision. Such a vision, of course, is a primary goal of Education for Sustainability.

References

- [1] Berry, T. (1988). *The dream of the earth*. San Francisco: Sierra Club Books.
- [2] Clark, Edward T. (1998). Guideline for designing a holistic school. In *Holistic education: principles, perspective, and practice*. Edited by Carol Flake, (121-131). Holistic education press.
- [3] Clark, Edward T. (2001). *Designing and Implementing an Integrated Curriculum: A Student-Centered Approach*
- [4] Forbes, S. (2003). *Holistic education: An analysis of its ideas in nature*. Brandon, VT: Foundation for Educational Renewal.
- [5] Grimes, B. (2007). *Multidimensional classroom: development a comprehensive research base for Holistic education*.
- [6] Hare, J. (2006). Toward an understanding of holistic education in the middle years of education. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 5(3), 23-25. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1475240906069453>
- [7] Miller, J. P. Ed. (2005). *Holistic learning and spirituality in education: Breaking new ground*. Albany: State University of New York Press. New York Press.
- [8] Miller, R. (1991a). Holism and meaning: Foundations for a coherent holistic theory. *Holistic Education Review*, 4(3), 23-31.
- [9] Miller, R. (2004) "Educational Alternatives: A Map of the Territory." *Paths of Learning*, 20, 20-27. [Online] Available: <http://pathsoflearning.org>
- [10] Nava, R. G. (2001). *Holistic education: Pedagogy of universal love*. Brandon: Holistic education press.
- [11] Rudge, L. T. (2008). *Holistic education: An analysis of its pedagogical application*. Dissertation, USA: University of Ohio.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON OUTCOME-BASED TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME FOR THE PRESENT CONTEXT

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Abstract

This article emphasis on outcome based teacher education programme for the present context. Teacher education is no exception. The learning outcome cannot be improved through wishful thinking. It needs strategic planning and careful implementation. Outcome-based education is an important response to this challenge. It is important to adopt Outcome-Based Teacher Education (OBTE) to improve learning outcomes in teacher education. Teacher Education is an integral part of higher education. There has been a phenomenal expansion of higher education; Outcome-based education is an innovation. Like any other innovation, this too disrupts the dynamic equilibrium of educational institution. It would upset the conventional practice of lecturing in the name of teaching, and more importantly, believing teaching is necessary for learning. With the focus on learning outcome, the OBTE would adopt multiple strategies for students to experiment, explore, resort to experiential learning, technology-enabled online and off-line learning, collaborative learning, etc.

Keywords: *Special Emphasis, Outcome Based Teacher Education Programme, Present Context*

Introduction

Teacher education is no exception. The learning outcome cannot be improved through wishful thinking. It needs strategic planning and careful implementation. Outcome-based education is an important response to this challenge. It is important to adopt Outcome-Based Teacher Education (OBTE) to improve learning outcomes in teacher education. Teacher Education is one department that knows why (foundations of education, especially psychological and socio-economical), how (the science of human learning, especially pedagogy and andragogy), and what (practices) of education. The interesting paradox is the gap between its knowledge and practice. Teacher education is fully familiar with the science of education; and how to improve the learning outcome of students. However, it does not practice what it preaches. It continues to practice the teacher-centric instructional (lecture) model while preaching student-centric activity-based learning to trainee teachers. Whether this is an incidental paradox or willful duplicity is a matter of research. Prospective teachers under training don't experience the science of human learning professed to them. They must live through (experience) the practices, they are advised to practice. Rightly, UGC has come out with a detailed 20-page document on learning outcome-based curriculum framework. Every teacher educator, preferably every teacher, should consult this document even if there are differences of opinion about the contents and approach of the UGC. There cannot be a difference of opinion that teacher education must change over from conventional to outcome-based teacher education.

Indian Higher Education

Teacher Education is an integral part of higher education. There has been a phenomenal expansion of higher education, especially during the last three decades. There are 907 universities, 39,701 colleges and 11923 standalone institutions (number may have already changed!). This massive expansion of the institutional network has increased access. The Indian higher education system today accommodates nearly 37.4 million students reaching a national GER of 26.3% (2018-19). India has set up a target of achieving 30% GER by 2020, and 50% by 2035. The achievement in access and equity in higher education is commendable. However, the crying concern continues to be poor quality. The crisis of quality in higher education is indicated by the fact that a large number of qualified engineers are not employable (Aspiring Minds 2019); more than 32% teachers already on the job are not employable (Mukhopadhyay and others, 2015). Less than 10% of university-qualified candidates succeed CTET and SETs. Thus, the qualified graduates from the universities do not provide enough evidence of learning. This higher education phenomenon of impressive achievement of access and equity without quality is

equally true for teacher education. Hence, adoption of outcome-based education in teacher education needs serious consideration.

Outcome-Based Education –A Glance

The outcome-based education is a system of education woven around predefined learning outcomes — what would a student be able to do on completion of a course or a programme.

In other words, learning outcome is the evidence or proof of learning. The relevant questions for understanding learning outcome are:

- 1) Can a medical surgeon successfully conduct the procedure of surgery on a patient?
- 2) Can an engineer scientifically design a project in the field of his or her specialization?
- 3) Can a mechanic actually conduct troubleshooting and repair a machine?
- 4) Can a qualified teacher successfully perform his or her role in assuring learning among students, assess student learning outcomes, provide guidance, plan instructional as well as co-scholastic and co-curricular activities, manage classrooms, examinations and or scholastic and co-curricular activities; manage interpersonal relations with parents, colleagues and students, etc.

Outcome-based education for teachers is especially important because teaching is no more communicating contents. There are other more powerful and effective means, quality learning resources, especially Open Education Repositories in text and digital contents as a source of information that was earlier served by textbooks and classroom lectures. The new challenge for the teacher is to be able to organize learning resources and opportunities for students, influence and inspire students; develop them as a learner and not learned or knowledgeable people. There is no one single specific style of teaching or assessment of learning outcomes; instead, classroom processes, other learning opportunities, and assessments should all help students achieve the specified learning outcomes.

Important point in Outcome-based Education is it is Learning Outcome Centric. The learning outcome is like the poll star. Curriculum Design, Learning Material and Learning Designs are informed by pre-specified learning outcome. In other words, these are designed to ensure achievement of learning outcome. Unlike in the conventional system, in OBE, the purpose of assessment is the assessment of learning outcomes. Learning outcome as the basis of designing a teacher education system has to respond to the following questions:

- 1) What would the student-trainee be able to do on completion of the teacher education programme? (Outcome)
- 2) What does a student-trainee need to learn (knowledge, skills and attitudes) in order to achieve the pre-specified learning outcome? (Curriculum)
- 3) What activities will facilitate achieving the learning outcome? (Pedagogy)
- 4) How will the student-trainee demonstrate the learning? (Assessment)
- 5) How would one judge whether the student-trainee has done well? (quality criteria)

UGC: Teacher Education Programme Outcome

- 1) Demonstrate core values such as (i) Commitment to the profession or job requirements; (ii) Honoring diversity and ensuring inclusion; (iii) Ethical integrity
- 2) Core competencies such as (i) communication skills; (ii) working effectively with students and their parents; and (iii) drive for achieving improved student learning outcomes.
- 3) Demonstrate professional/technical knowledge of the physical, social and intellectual development and characteristics of students
- 4) Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of strategies for differentiating teaching to meet the specific learning needs of students
- 5) Demonstrate knowledge required to design learning sequences and lesson;
- 6) Demonstrate professional competencies/practice that is required to select and use relevant teaching strategies to develop knowledge, skills, problem-solving and critical and creative thinking;
- 7) Select and/or create and use a range of resources, including ICT;
- 8) Demonstrate professional competencies/ practice that is required to manage classroom activities;
- 9) Demonstrate professional competencies/ practice to develop, select and use informal and formal, diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies; and
- 10) Demonstrate competencies and actions required for keeping oneself professionally engaged and participate in learning to update knowledge and practice”

Implementing OBE in Teacher Education

Outcome-based education is an innovation. Like any other innovation, this too disrupts the dynamic equilibrium of educational institution. It would upset the conventional practice of lecturing in the name of teaching, and more importantly, believing teaching is necessary for learning. With the focus on learning outcome, the OBTE would adopt multiple strategies for students to experiment, explore, resort to experiential learning, technology-enabled online and off-line learning, collaborative learning, etc. This new ways of learning will completely upset existing instructional practices in the teacher education institutions. There is enough research evidence that indicates that bottom-up innovations are often lost on the way as its success depends upon the enthusiasm of the innovator. The innovator is often challenged and questioned by other colleagues. The countervailing conventional forces challenge the forces of innovation. The top-down innovation runs the risk of getting deformed as unwilling implementers adapt it to suit their convenience.

Conclusion

This article concludes that special emphasis needed for outcome based teacher education course for the present context. As mentioned in the beginning, teacher education is one department in a university that knows the science and art of improvement of learning outcome. Unless this tacit knowledge is converted into explicit practices, teacher education will continue to be a backbencher in the universities despite their potential to lead the universities in educational reforms. Implementing outcome-based teacher education holds the promise for a paradigm shift for ushering in quality teacher education.

DEVELOPMENT OF ICT BASED LEARNING MATERIALS FOR ENHANCING MAP READING SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Introduction

Today the world around us is witnessed with a bizarre of hi-tech advancements. Blending of e-Tools with Instructional Procedure is an Innovative Educational Paradigm. the present status of Geography teaching it is very well observed that there are lapses in the textbook methods of teaching that are either stereotyped or outdated. the study intended to prepare an ICT based learning material that would develop both map reading skills among secondary school students reflecting a 'warm, welcoming and encouraging approach child-centered and activity-based process of learning skills organized through practice' as expected by the National Policy on Education (1986).

Need and Significance

Maps play an important role in developing understanding of Geography. But, to make use of the map as a tool, one need to develop the skill to read, draw and mark on maps - which are acquired by normally under the guidance of a teacher. While examining the present status of Geography teaching it is very well observed that there are lapses in the textbook methods of teaching that are either stereotyped or outdated. ICT based learning material that would develop both map reading skills among secondary school students reflecting a 'warm, welcoming, Encouraging approach child-centered and activity-based process of learning skills organized through practice. It also proposed to validate the Instructional Programme in terms of its effectiveness in developing map skills and understandings and to compare its effectiveness with the conventional approach to teaching Geography. The attitude of the students towards the alternate approach to teaching Geography was also interpreted.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To prepare an ICT based learning material to develop selected map reading skills in secondary school students.
- 2) To study the effectiveness of the prepared ICT learning material in terms of developing map reading skills.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) The practice of using ICT based learning material can enhance the students map reading skills in secondary school students.
- 2) The ICT aids are more effective than the traditional aids in terms of developing map reading skills and understandings in Geography.

Methodology

Methodology involves the procedure adopted for the realisation of the objectives of the study. The objectives of the present study the investigator develop an ICT based learning material to develop selected map reading skills in secondary school students. A brief description of the method adopted for the study, the sample selected and tools used for the study, the procedure of the study and the statistical techniques adopted is given below. Method adopted for the study: The investigator adopted experimental method for the present study, for the investigator develop an ICT based learning material to develop selected map reading skills in secondary school students. The design used for the present study was single group pre- test and post-test design. Sample for the study: The sample of a study means the participants in a study. It is a small portion of the population selected for the data collection. The investigator selected 30 students studying in VIIth standard from St. Goretti HS. School, Nalanchira (Thiruvananthapuram district). Tools used for the study: Achievement Tests on Map Reading Skills & ICT based learning material. Statistical technique: Arithmetic mean & Standard deviation. Procedure for the Data Collection: This study was conducted in 30 sample students from St. Goretti HS, Nalanchira. Investigated developed ICT based maps reading items for this particular study. This study was conducted on VIIIth standard

students. And the result was analyzed using score based on the achievement test of the students.

Major Findings of the Study

The mean score of the pre-test was 13. And the post-test was 16.7 2. In the pre-test, it was found that 23.33% (7) students have above average on mapping reading skills. 56.67% (17) students have average map reading skills. Only 6 (20%) have a below-average map reading skill. After providing the ICT based learning material developed by the instigator to the students, there was a wide increase in the results of the post-test administered. In the post-test, it was analysed that 46.67 % (14) students have above average on mapping reading skills. 40 % (12) students have average map reading skills. Only 4 (13.33%) have below-average map reading skill.

Educational Implications

The present study demonstrated the effectiveness of the ICT based learning material which develops map reading skills and understanding student's comprehensive learning abilities in Geography among the secondary school students. Today's generation is digital natives therefore, they are more convenient with technological aid more than the traditional aids. In early times, most of us using Atlas for map references but now the situation is different most of us using google and all other online source for the references. It also points out that the developed material is feasible from two perspective point of view - one, it can be fitted into the existing Geography curriculum and two, it is perceived favourably by the students who are exposed. The present study could be more useful and effective, especially from the point of view of developing understandings in Geography content as well as strengthening of maps reading skill through ICT based learning materials.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated the effectiveness of the ICT based learning material which develops map reading skills and understanding student's comprehensive learning abilities in Geography among the secondary school students. The present study could be more useful and effective, especially from the points of view of developing understandings in Geography content as well as strengthening of maps reading skill through ICT based learning materials.

References

- [1] Anderson, I.M., (1955): Step in Map Reading, Rand Mc Nally & co., Chicago.
- [2] David Woodward (2007), The history of cartography, The University of Chicago Press, USA.
- [3] Gurjar, RD., (2001): A hand Book for Geography Teachers, ABD publishers, Jaipur. 4. Rai, B.C., (1979): Teaching of Geography, Prakash Kendra, Lucknow.
- [4] Thamarasseri Ismail (2012); Teaching of Social Science for the 21st Century, Kanishka Publishers & Distributors, New Delhi.
- [5] Singh Kulbir, (1983): Methodology of research in education, sterling publishers Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi.
- [6] Castner, H., (1990), seeks new Horizons, A Perceptual approach to Geographic Education, McGill-Queen's University Press, Montreal.
- [7] SCERT, Kerala (2018); Social Science Class VIII Text Book, Dept. of Education, Kerala.
- [8] NCERT, (2019); Our Environment Textbook in geography for class VII, Publication Division by the Secretary, National Council of Educational Research and Training, Sri Aurobindo Marg, New Delhi 110016 and printed at Fauji Printing Press, Khasra, No.24/20 Nangli Shakrawati Industrial Area, Najafgarh, New Delhi-110043.

IMPLEMENTATION OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING APPROACH IN FLIPPED CLASSROOM

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Abstract

This paper focuses the implementation of cooperative learning approach in flipped learning classroom environment. In this article the author analyzes the suitable type of cooperative approach for implementing in flipped class. This article points out the sorry state of traditional class hours for not focusing creative expression in the classroom. Even though flipped classroom provides the creative opportunity to the students, it also focuses the online learning only not the social interaction. To shine the flipped classroom with social interaction with their peers, the author created and suggested three models for the implementation of cooperative learning approach in flipped classroom. This paper also discusses the uses and limitation of the three different models with different perspective. This article may help the researchers and the teachers those who are studying and practicing cooperative learning and flipped learning.

Keywords: *Cooperative Learning, Flipped Learning, Models of Implementation*

Introduction

Cooperative learning is an active learning approach which helps to learn in a group. It encourages not only to learn and also to teach. It gives the opportunity to construct the knowledge with the discussion of the peers. In a traditional classroom teacher takes the major role from selecting the content to evaluating the students' learning. But cooperative classroom emphasize the students' role to construct the knowledge with the light of given resource material along with the group members. Another important activity learning approach is the flipped learning approach. It involves the tremendous change in students learning behavior and classroom structure. In a traditional classroom teaching, teacher focuses mainly with cognitive domain only. But flipped learning provides the opportunity to make the classroom as a studio. These above two approaches makes the classroom environment actively. Now a days it triggers the mind of the researchers to apply the cooperative approach in a flipped classroom environment. Thus this article also discuss the implementation of cooperative learning with flipped classroom.

Cooperative Approach in Flipped Classroom

Normally we used the cooperative learning approach in the traditional classroom environment. It means to support the traditional classroom with the help of cooperative approach. But we can apply the cooperative approach in flipped classroom environment. Even though flipped classroom is more effective than traditional classroom, learning happens through individual effort. We can also make our flipped classroom more effectively with the implementation of cooperative approach.

Suitable Type of Cooperative Group in Flipped Classroom

Before implement the cooperative approach in flipped class we must understand the types of cooperative approach. Commonly Cooperative learning groups can be classified into three groups. There are:

- 1) Informal Cooperative Learning
- 2) Formal Cooperative Learning
- 3) Cooperative Based Groups

Informal Cooperative Learning Groups

This type of cooperative learning groups are short term basis and ad-hoc groups in which students are required to work together to achieve a shared learning goal. Informal cooperative learning may be used to help students engage in the learning task, and focus their attention on the material they are to learn through focused-pair discussions before and after a lecture.

Formal Cooperative Learning Groups

Formal cooperative learning groups last from one class period to several weeks. These are cooperative learning groups in which students work together to complete the learning tasks assigned and achieve shared learning goals.

Cooperative Based Groups

Cooperative based groups usually last a semester or an academic year, or even several years. They are long-term and heterogeneous learning groups with committed relationships, in which students support one another to complete assignments and make academic progress. From the above three types of the group teacher may choose any one of the type to implement in flipped classroom. But author of this article suggest to implement the formal cooperative learning groups for the following reasons.

Reason to Select Formal Learning Group

Informal Learning group focuses on only the lecture given by the teacher. It shrinks with a particular class hour only. So it may not helpful to extent the learning process out of the class hours. And then author also avoids the cooperative based groups. Because it expect the whole year to learn. Flipped learning approach is the recent developing approach to learn. Students, teachers, parents, administrators are not familiar with flipped leaning environment it can't be reachable and practicable throughout the year. So author suggest the formal cooperative learning groups can be allowed to implement. In this type of groups students are organized to complete the task during the period of one or two weeks.

Bloom's and Revised Bloom's Taxonomy

In a traditional classroom we try to use all the domains of Bloom's taxonomy, but we are restricted with time limit and syllabus completion target. So that many of the traditional classroom focused cognitive aspect only. In cognitive aspect itself the major evaluation parts are taking place in their home environment not in classroom. But flipped approach involves the revised Bloom's Taxonomy in the sense of synthesis and evaluation in the classroom situation.

Models of Implementing Cooperative Learning in Flipped Classroom

The conceptual foundations of flipped learning are based on simply not teaching the lessons in a classroom environment and on student-centered learning theories. This is the inversion of traditional classroom. Traditional classes focus the teacher centered teaching and gives more importance to cognitive domain only. In cognitive domain itself it gives the less importance to evaluation. But flipped classroom totally change the learning situation. It makes the classroom as a studio on what they had learnt in their home from the video lectures which was shared by the teacher. They has enthusiastically participate to complete the task, making posters on their learnt material, preparing charts, etc.

Model 1

In this model for implementing cooperative learning approach in flipped classroom students are learning individually with the video material shared by the teacher on a particular content. Next day students are grouped by the teacher to discuss about their previous learning with the group members and creating posters or making charts.

Model 2

In this Model students are grouped with 3-5 members for online learning by the teacher in the class hours and the video lesson will be sent to the online group. In the home environment students are learning through online group. But next day students will individually expose what they have learnt in their online group.

Model 3

In this model students are learning in their home with their online group (3-5 members) on the video material which was sent by the teacher. Here students can also plan for the next day presentations. Next day students present their group creations in their classroom.

Discussion on the Models

The first model allows the students to learn individually in their home environment on the shared video material and they discussed with the group members in the classroom. This model facilitates to selecting the learning time independently rather than other models. The second model and third model making the students' learning time depends with other person in the group. But the second model motivates to learn together with the group and verify their learning through the individual presentation in the classroom environment. The third model provides the opportunity to learn with group in home environment and express their group's understanding and creativity in the classroom. From this discussion we can find the following results:

- 1) Model 1 gives the confirmation of the group members and whole class on the individuals own understanding on the video materials.
- 2) Model 2 develops the students to present individually in the classroom on the video material which they have learnt in online group. It stimulates the individual performance.
- 3) Model 3 focuses the team learning and team working. This team spirit develops the competitive attitude with other groups.

Conclusion

Through this article we can understand the implementation of cooperative learning approach in flipped classroom. It also discussed the suitable type of cooperative learning to implement in flipped class. It figures out three models of implementing along with the discussion. In accordance of implementing cooperative learning in flipped classroom very few studies are there. So author of this article suggest the research people to study the implementation of cooperative learning in flipped learning.

AN NN MODEL FOR TIME SERIES FORECASTING TO PREDICT THE RETURN OF STOCK INDEX

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Abstract

Generating accurate Predictions of Financial Market movements has always been a key goal for all stakeholders of an economy. The various algorithms used for time series forecasting. It can be categorized into linear model (ARIMA, ARMA) and non-linear models (neural network). A linear regression model is not suitable for time series because these model are neglected a problems on time. It adds additional information that makes time series problems even more difficult to handle .The traditional model used to predict time series like autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average model (SARIMA) but this model is not sufficient for time series .that's why Neural Networks (NN) is important essential for time series forecasting. Only certain type of Neural Networks Suitable for time series model .Such as Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short- Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks. These machine learning models that enable better predictions by improving the accuracy of time series. In this paper , different time series models are taken and compare them with neural networks for predict the returns for the S&P500 (Standard & Poor's 500) index .This paper also concludes that neural networks is suited for time series forecasting. The experiments were executed in jupyter notebook 6.0.3 .the codes and simulations were implemented using python 3.6.5 with a dependency of tensorflow 1.15.0 and keras 2.3.1

Keywords: *Neural Networks - Time Series Forecasting - Returns of Stock Index*

Introduction

The Stock Market refers to the collection of markets and exchanges where regular activities of buying, selling, and issuance of shares of publicly-held companies take place. When we talk about Indian Stock Exchanges, most of the investing population has heard of two stock exchanges in India Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE). A Stock Exchange is a place or platform which hosts a market where buyers and sellers come together to trade stocks during specific hours of business days. A stock or share also known as a company's equity is a financial instrument that represents ownership in a company or corporation and represents a proportionate claim on its assets what it owns and earnings what it generates in profits. The share prices are set by supply and demand in the market as buyers and sellers place orders. An index measures the price of stock and performance of a basket of securities using a standardized metric and methodology. A passive index investing has become a popular low-cost way to replicate the returns of popular indices such as the S&P 500. The S&P 500 indexes or the Standard & Poor's 500 index is a market-capitalization-weighted index of the 500 largest U.S publicly traded companies. The S&P is a float-weighted index, meaning company market capitalizations are adjusted by the number of shares available for public trading. As a result, there are many funds designed to track the performance of the S&P. Time Series Forecasting is a technique for the prediction of events through a sequence of time. The techniques predict future events by analyzing the trends of the past on the assumption that future trends will hold similar to historical trends. Time series forecasting starts with a historical time series. It analysts examine the historical data and check for patterns of time decomposition. Neural Networks generates the best possible result without needing to redesign the output criteria. Neural network helps to predict time series forecasting. Because its easy-to-extract features, good at extracting patterns easily, support for multiple inputs and outputs, easy to predict from training data in Financial Market.

Literature survey

In this research study, the following models are taken for literature study and are compared with proposed models. Linear Regression- It is a Statistical Method for examining the relationship between a dependent variable, denoted as Y and one or More Independent Variables, denoted as X [13]. The problem with Linear Regression, It's a dependent variable, it usually affected by the independent variables. Linear Regression is limited to linear relationships. It only looks at the mean of the dependent variable and also linear regression is sensitive to outlier. ARIMA -Based on Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, or ARIMA, is a forecasting method for univariate time series data [3]. It supports both an autoregressive and moving average elements. The integrated element refers to differencing allowing the method to support time series data with a trend. A Problem with ARIMA is that it does not support seasonal data. That is a time series with a repeating cycle. ARIMA expects data that is either not

seasonal or has the seasonal component removed [5]. SARIMA -Based on Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, or SARIMA, is an extension of ARIMA that explicitly supports univariate time series data with a seasonal component [14]. The problem with SARIMA model is, it can only extract linear relationships within the time series data. Neural Network -A Neural Network is a series of algorithms that endeavors to recognize underlying relationships in a set of data through a process that mimics the way the human brain operates. Neural Networks are potentially useful endemic time series forecasting methods because of their strong nonlinear mapping ability and tolerance to complexity in forecasting data. They are especially useful when a nonlinear relationship exists within the time series data.

Related Work

Before deep learning era financial time series modeling has mainly concentrated in the linear model. Any modifications on this model and the result have proved that the traditional time series model does provide decent predictive power to a limit forecasting. The work showed that provided more accurate forecasts than the back-propagation of a neural network [11][9]. Recently deep learning methods have demonstrated better performances when compare to linear model. Because of the improved computational power and the ability of learning non-linear relationships enclosed in various financial features [6]. Compared different deep learning architectures including LSTM and CNN models for the prediction of stocks index they concluded that CNN architecture is capable of identifying changes in trend of stocks and outperforms other models.

Proposed Work

Data and Methodology

This analysis involves information on the stock indices of S&P500 covering the period from 2000 to 2020 and having a total number of 7661 observations. On the idea of this information, to determine various time series model to predict the returns for the S&P500 index. The proposed work focus on EDA (Exploratory Data Analysis). EDA Process Specifically Focuses on Understanding Characters of Data, Finding Meaningful Patters in Data, Possible Modeling Strategies, Debugging Strategies and Visualization of Results.

Figure 1: Exploratory Data Analysis

The Data Set Contains Thousands of Electronics Store Purchases Broken down by Month, Product Type, Cost, Purchase, etc.

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Table 1: S & P 500 index Data Set

date	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: 100	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: SENSEX	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: 200	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: Dollex-200	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: 500	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: Information Technology	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: Capital Goods	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: Fast Moving Consumer Goods	Bombay Stock Exchange: Index: Consumer Durables	...	National Stock Exchange: Index: Nifty 500	National Stock Exchange: PE Ratio: Nifty 50	National Stock Exchange: PB Ratio: Nifty 50
2000-01-03	1636.49	5375.11	635.04	243.17	1920.08	4260.20	1196.46	1172.50	1526.33	...	1291.55	25.91	4.63
2000-01-04	1690.67	5491.01	652.91	249.89	1972.29	4554.08	1179.47	1138.74	1517.65	...	1335.45	26.67	4.76
2000-01-05	1643.14	5357.00	636.89	243.65	1922.87	4342.29	1145.40	1116.22	1470.10	...	1303.80	25.97	4.64
2000-01-06	1644.78	5421.53	636.96	243.68	1923.36	4160.10	1174.28	1168.77	1531.15	...	1306.60	26.32	4.70
2000-01-07	1606.46	5414.48	620.91	237.59	1871.82	3828.79	1138.47	1207.37	1497.40	...	1276.30	26.25	4.69
2020-02-24	11941.07	40363.23	4989.47	1156.22	15469.29	16176.41	16374.24	11308.68	26874.39	...	9758.20	26.92	3.33
2020-02-25	11903.01	40281.20	4972.74	1151.86	15418.71	16270.52	16262.28	11306.25	26572.20	...	9724.70	26.85	3.32
2020-02-26	11777.28	39888.96	4919.40	1143.14	15256.99	16022.85	15921.25	11238.48	26442.94	...	9622.70	26.58	3.29

5258 rows x 61 columns

Data Stationary

It's a property of time series data stating that the distributional properties (mean and standard deviation) of the data series have not changed across time for forecasting. It's important that the data be stationary because in the absence of stationary, one is asking the model to predict data that is nothing like anything it has seen before. A Common Test of Stationary is The Dickey-Fuller Test. Such as if the P-Value associated with the Dickey-Fuller Test Statistic is Greater than 0.05, State that the Data Is Not Stationary.

Figure 2: Without Data Stationary for S & P 500 index

From the above results, the p-value is 0.964552; leading to the conclusion that the nifty500 index series is not stationary. It can be further seen more clearly from the graph. The clear upward trend of the rolling mean and rolling standard deviation signals that nifty500 is not stationary. To make the data as stationary as possible: the easiest ways of making the data stationary is to calculate the first difference for level variables (like indices) .the first difference in the percentage change in relation to the previous time period. For percentage variables, it's the value of the variable in the current time period subtracted from the value of the variables at the previous date.

Rolling Mean & Standard Deviation for National Stock Exchange: Index: Nifty 500Ret

```
Results of Dickey-Fuller Test:
Test Statistic      -1.741829e+01
p-value             4.842084e-30
# Lags Used         1.300000e+01
Number of Observations Used  5.243000e+03
Critical Value (1%)  -3.431598e+00
Critical Value (5%)  -2.862091e+00
Critical Value (10%) -2.567064e+00
dtype: float64
```

Figure 3: With Data Stationary for S & P 500 index

From the above graph, the percentage change in nifty 500 indexes is stationary as the p-value is less than 0.05. again, for greater intuition look at the graph - the rolling mean and rolling standard deviation lines are almost flat meaning that they don't change in a statistically significant manner over time.

Training, Validation and Testing

The objective of a machine learning methods is to predict the dependent variable as accurately as possible. To minimize the predicted error (the difference between the actual value and predicted value), to measure the predictive accuracy of a model, it is important that the forecast accuracy be measured out-of-sample as the training accuracy can be made arbitrarily high through over fitting. If we use the entire out-of-sample data for testing, we may over fit to the out-of-sample data (data leakage), resulting poor true generalizability. To protect against 'data leakage', split the out-of-sample data into two parts: validation data and testing data. The training, validation and testing data can be organized in many ways such as, Cross Validation: Bootstrap sampling for cross sectional methods but not suited for time series. Fixed Window: Training, Validation and Testing Periods Demarcated By Dates. Rolling Window: Shifting a Window of Fixed Size - By One Observation Successively Expanding Window - Increasing the Window Size by 1 Successively.

Rescaling Normalized Data

Normalize the data in the training sample because machine learning methods are not scale invariant. Scale it to being between -1 and 1 as that is the appropriate scaling for data when being input into a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) And Long Short Term Memory Network (LSTM). Here scaling for all the methods to make the prediction errors comparable.

Metric to be used to Gauge Accuracy of Forecasts

The most commonly used metric for gauging the accuracy of time series forecasts is the **Mean Squared Error (MSE)**.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

The higher the MSE, the worse is the predictive accuracy of the model. Thus for each model, it is desired that the MSE be minimized.

Experimental Results

After training the model, the result of testing has shown different results. The proposed work uses data from the past to predict the return on the dataset. To assess the model, our primary model performance metric is Mean Squared Error (MSE). The MSE will be performed on the test data, which is totally unseen from the training and development stages. It is calculated between our predicted price and the true price.

Linear Model - ARIMA / SARIMA model

ARIMA models describe how each successive observation is related to the previous observation [6]. The seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) is capable of modeling the seasonal components in a univariate time series in addition to the autoregressive, moving average and trend components typically modeled by ARIMA.

Figure 4: Result of ARIMA / SARIMA MODEL

Based on above results we face challenges on ARIMA models. They are generally poor at predicting turning points. As the number of steps forecasted ahead in the future increases, the forecast converges to the mean. The model of ARIMA and SARIMA, where no differencing was performed to change the stationarity. However, the model gave a linear prediction from test data, even the forecasted trend is opposite to the real price trend. The results suggested ARIMA model did not perform well in predicting non-linearity and long- term prediction.

Neural Network Model

Here We Consider Two Methods:

- 1) Dimensional Convolutional Neural Networks (**1D-CNNs**)
- 2) Long Short Term Memory (**LSTM**) Networks

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Model

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) can extract information from the temporal structure of the data by preserving the spatial/ temporal structure of the data in the input layer. Using filters which look for patterns in

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spatially adjacent data. For instance, one filter could find speaks, another could find troughs while another could find a linear trend. The information extracted by the filters is known as a Feature Map. Each additional feature results in a new feature map extracting a more complex feature. For a time series dataset, a filter can only move along 1 dimension – time. The CNN Layer may be followed by a sub-sampling layer which reduces the noise in the learned features (i.e. the feature maps). The Sub-Sampling Layer is followed by a Regression Layer.

CNN Model Train Start

```
Train on 4693 samples, validate on 128 samples
Epoch 1/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.1225 - val_loss: 0.0313
Epoch 2/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0532 - val_loss: 0.0297
Epoch 3/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0473 - val_loss: 0.0278
Epoch 4/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0439 - val_loss: 0.0242
Epoch 5/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0407 - val_loss: 0.0250
Epoch 6/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0388 - val_loss: 0.0222
Epoch 7/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0361 - val_loss: 0.0212
Epoch 8/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0349 - val_loss: 0.0208
```

CNN Model Train End

```
Epoch 420/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 421/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 422/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 423/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 424/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 425/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 426/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
Epoch 427/100000
- 1s - loss: 0.0096 - val_loss: 0.0023
```

CNN Results

Model: "sequential_1"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv1d_1 (Conv1D)	(None, 15, 5)	6005
max_pooling1d_1 (MaxPooling1D)	(None, 15, 5)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 15, 5)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 75)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	76

Total params: 6,081
Trainable params: 6,081
Non-trainable params: 0

Figure 6: Result of CNN MODEL

Based on the above results the MSE is reduced compared to ARIMA/SARIMA model.

Long Short Term Memory Network (LSTM)

A CNNs for time series data is that they do not draw information from the sequential nature of independent data. LSTM networks draw information from the sequential nature of the data because they have memory. i.e. it remembers what it has seen. LSTMs build short and long term memories by revealing data to the hidden nodes in a sequential. Each LSTM node is comprised of LSTM cells. The long term and short term memory is updated in each LSTM cell upon being exposed to each subsequent element of the sequence, conditional on the output of each 'gate'. Gate is a neural network with a sigmoid/logistic activation function which determines how the memory updated by accepting as inputs as the current elements x of the sequence and the outputs of the previous LSTM cell i.e. the long term memory and hidden memory from the previous member of the sequence.

LSTM Model Training Start

```
[0.5488135 0.71518937 0.60276338 0.54488318]
Train on 4693 samples, validate on 128 samples
Epoch 1/100000
- 20s - loss: 0.3244 - val_loss: 0.0025
Epoch 2/100000
- 20s - loss: 0.0280 - val_loss: 0.0027
Epoch 3/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0254 - val_loss: 0.0027
Epoch 4/100000
- 23s - loss: 0.0240 - val_loss: 0.0028
Epoch 5/100000
- 23s - loss: 0.0235 - val_loss: 0.0027
Epoch 6/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0225 - val_loss: 0.0025
Epoch 7/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0223 - val_loss: 0.0026
Epoch 8/100000
- 23s - loss: 0.0214 - val_loss: 0.0030
Epoch 9/100000
```

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LSTM Model Train End

```

Epoch 149/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0100 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 150/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0100 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 151/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0098 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 152/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0099 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 153/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0099 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 154/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0100 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 155/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0100 - val_loss: 0.0022
Epoch 156/100000
- 22s - loss: 0.0100 - val_loss: 0.0022
    
```

Result of LSTM

Model: "sequential_2"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm_1 (LSTM)	(None, 300)	1081200
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 300)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 1)	301

Total params: 1,081,501
 Trainable params: 1,081,501
 Non-trainable params: 0

Figure 7: Result of LSTM MODEL

Table 2: Performance Analysis

Name of the Model	Type of Relation	Accuracy of MSE (In terms of %)	
		Result of Validation	Result of Test
ARIMA/SARIMA	Linear	0.28	0.38

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CNN	Non Linear	0.21	0.33
LSTM	Non Linear	0.22	0.33

In Table 2, shows that each model was trained for each stock and the MSE for the testing sample are performed on each of stocks. Comparison of the results from each model predicts that CNN and LSTM perform better than both traditional models as expected. As for long-term time series prediction, the Neural Networks brings advantages of selecting the important and relevant information hence enhancing the predictive accuracy.

Conclusion

In proposed system, NEURAL NETWORK is used for predicting the stock price. Here, trained the model for predict the stock index price from the obtained results; it is quite obvious that these models are reasonably efficient in recognizing the patterns that exists in the stock market. This shows that there is an underlying dynamics, which is very common to all the stock markets. The linear series models such as ARIMA/SARIMA time-series based prediction models and they are incapable in recognizing the under dynamics with the help of multivariate time series. Hence from the results obtained, Neural Network proved as a better performer when compared to other model by implemented CNN and LSTM Neural Networks for time-series prediction problems. CNN and LSTM neural networks are best suited for time series forecasting. The deep learning model might possibly apply in other areas as well as in the future.

Reference

- [1] M.R. Amer, B. Siddiquie, C. Richey, and A. Divakaran, "Emotion detection in speech using deep networks.", IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) , pp.3724-3728, IEEE, 2014.
- [2] Y. Bengio, "Learning deep architectures for AI. Foundations and trends in Machine Learning" vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1-127, 2009
- [3] Bijesh Dhyani, Manish Kumar, Poonam Verma, Abhisheik Jain, "Stock Market Forecasting Technique using Arima "International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ,ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-6, March 2020
- [4] G.E. Box, G.M. Jenkins, G.C. Reinsel, and G.M. Ljung, " Time series analysis: forecasting and control.", Holden-Day, 1976.
- [5] B. Choi, "ARMA model identification", Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [6] Hiransha M , Gopalakrishnan E,"NSE Stock Market Prediction Using Deep-Learning Models"
- [7] ScienceDirect, Procedia Computer Science 132 (2018) 1351–1362
- [8] G.E. Hinton, et al, "Deep neural networks for acoustic modeling in speech recognition: The sharedviews of four research groups". IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 82-97, 2012.
- [9] J.J.M. Moreno, A.P. Pol, and P.M. Gracia, "Artificial neural networks applied to forecasting time series.", Psicothema, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 322-329. 2011.
- [10] Ramaswamy Seethalakshmi,"Analysis of stock market predictor variables using Linear Regression", International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, January 2018,119(15)

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STRESS MANAGEMENT THROUGH YOGA

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Abstract

In today's Business World Stress is an expected part of life. How we deal with our stress is important to our overall well-being. Stress is associated with our reaction to the external environment as well as our inner thoughts and feelings. No one can live without experiencing some degree of stress all the time. Some people feel stress in shoulder and neck muscles or in the lower back, others have difficulty in sleeping, or concentration on day to day tasks. During times of increased stress, our body's nutrients are used more rapidly to meet these needs. So, we require increased amounts of many of these nutrients. The antioxidant vitamins A, E and C, the B vitamins and the minerals Zinc, Selenium, Calcium, Magnesium, Iron, Potassium, Sulfur are some Nutrients that are commonly depleted by Stress. Learning to control our thoughts through meditation. Yoga and other mind quieting techniques can be very helpful in reducing Stress levels. In this paper, exposes the Causes, Signs, Types, Disorder, Stress Handling and Management through Yoga Exercises.

Introduction

Stress is not even necessarily bad for you; it is also the spice of life; for any emotion, any activity causes Stress. But, of course, our system must be prepared for it. Some people especially those in the business world, Stress Management sounds better. Perhaps it's the perception of the word relaxation. Pictures of sitting around and doing nothing spring to mind. We called it as "Stress Management" it implies taking action. Stress Management sounds efficient. It makes a better marketing package. Today stress management programs have grown up and matured. Public sector are recognizing that a comprehensive program should include proper diet, exercise and rest along with other stress-reduction techniques. Stress Management programs are now being offered with a balanced approach.

Common Cause of Stress

Stress can arise for a variety of reasons. Stress can be brought about by a traumatic accident, death, or emergency situation. Stress can also be a side of a serious illness or disease. There is also stress associated with daily life, the workplace and family responsibilities. It's hard to stay calm and relaxed in our hectic lives. Stress can take on many different forms, and can contribute to symptoms of illness. Common symptoms include headache, sleep disorder, lack of concentration and short-temper, upset stomach, Job Dissatisfaction, Low Morale, Depression and Anxiety.

Types of Stress

Everyone has stress. We have Short-Term Stress, like getting lost while driving or missing the bus. Even everyday events, such as planning a meal or making time for errands, can be stressful. This kind of stress can make us feel worried or anxious. We face Long-Term Stress, such as racial discrimination, a life-threatening illness, or divorce. These stressful events also affect our health on many levels. Long-term stress is real and can increase our risk for some health problems, like depression. Both Short and Long-Term Stress can have effects on our body. Stress triggers changes in our bodies and makes us more likely to get sick. It can make problems we already have worse. It can play a part in these problems:

- 1) Trouble sleeping
- 2) Headaches
- 3) Constipation
- 4) Diarrhea
- 5) Irritability
- 6) Lack of energy
- 7) Lack of concentration
- 8) Eating too much or not at all
- 9) Anger
- 10) Sadness
- 11) High risk of asthma and arthritis flare-ups
- 12) Tension
- 13) Stomach cramping
- 14) Stomach bloating
- 15) Skin problems, like hives

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- 16) Depression
- 17) Anxiety
- 18) Weight gain or loss
- 19) Heart problem
- 20) High blood pressure
- 21) Irritable bowel syndrome
- 22) Diabetes
- 23) Neck and/ or back pain
- 24) Less sexual desire
- 25) Harder to get pregnant

Most Stressful Event

Any change in our lives can be stressful events some of the happiest ones like having a baby or taking a new job. Here are some of life's most stressful events.

- 1) Death of a spouse
- 2) Divorce
- 3) Martial separation
- 4) Spending time in jail.
- 5) Death of a Close Family Member.
- 6) Personal illness or Injury.
- 7) Marriage
- 8) Pregnancy
- 9) Retirement

Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)

Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) can be debilitating condition that can occur after exposure to a terrifying event that can ordeal in which grave physical harm occurred or was threatened. Traumatic events that can trigger PTSD include violent personal assault such as rape or mugging, natural or human-caused disaster, accidents, or military combat. Many people with PTSD repeatedly re experience the ordeal in the form of flash back episodes, memories, nightmares, or frightening thoughts, especially when they are exposed to events or objects that remind them of the trauma. People with PTSD also can have emotional numbness, sleep disturbances, depression, anxiety, irritability, or outbursts of anger. Most people who are exposed to a traumatic, stressful event have some symptoms generally disappear. But about 8% of men and 20% of women go on to develop PTSD, and roughly 30% of these people develop a chronic, or long-lasting, form that persists throughout their lives.

Healthy Ways for Stress Handling

Don't let stress make our sick. As women, we tend to carry higher burden of stress than we should. Often, we aren't even aware of our stress levels. Listens to our body, so that we know when stress is affecting human health. Here are ways to help to handle the stress.

- 1) Relax
- 2) Make time for yourself
- 3) Sleep
- 4) Eat right
- 5) Get moving
- 6) Talk to friends
- 7) Get help from a professional if you need it
- 8) Compromise
- 9) Write down your thoughts
- 10) Help others
- 11) Get a hobby
- 12) Set limits
- 13) Play your time
- 14) Don't deal with stress in unhealthy ways

Stress Management Through Yoga

Yoga is a physical and mental process designed to bring the practitioner's body and mind together. People of any fitness level can practice yoga, not just the extremely flexible. The yoga exercise is for use by all body types, or philosophies. Learn and practice these exercises, and not only we will be able to say, "I practice yoga." We will able to say, "I have found a method to control my stress." The first and most important yogic exercise is shavasana, or "corpse pose." It is both a physical and mental exercise. The point is to completely relax the body so that it resembles an actual corpse. The mind is also stilled. Thoughts are not

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allowed. In this way the mind is relaxed, and purified. Below are the essential steps to this exercise.

- 1) Lie on your back with your eyes closed. You should be comfortable and on a flat surface. We only prefer on a carpeted floor or on a yoga mat.
- 2) Position your arms about two feet from your body with your palms up.
- 3) Spread your feet about a foot apart.
- 4) To release tension in your neck, turn your head from side to side.
- 5) Now begin to consciously relax. Start with the toes, and move up the body. Repeat until all parts are relaxed. This may be difficult the first time. You may want to be yourself, "I am relaxed, completely relaxed." You may also want to tell an uncooperative part of you to give in by saying, "Relax lower back!"
- 6) Feel and hear your breathing. Do not force or try to control it. Consider it an entity on itself.
- 7) Relax your mind. If thoughts drift in and out, simply ignore them. Picture them as leaves on a river. Allow them to drift away from you.
- 8) Continue to observe your breath, if this is a challenge use the sound "OOMM" to redirect your focus on stillness. This is a "Mantra." A mantra is a sound a yogi uses to evoke certain energies while meditating. This one represents the universe translated to sound.
- 9) Continue your focus on breath until you have achieved the amount of relaxation on stillness you desire. To bring yourself out of the trance-like state this meditation induces, begin to allow your thoughts to remain with you, and let your breathing become more controlled.

Steps to Reduce Stress

- 1) Make a list of stress trigger and learn how to recognize them. Consciously try to recognize them and learn to relax in these situations.
- 2) Always be careful to be cheerful.
- 3) When feeling stressed try to relax by slowing down the thoughts, breathe in peace.....
Breathe out stress.
- 4) Take regular breaks from work if working at home.
- 5) Reduce tension by allowing the self more leisure time. Become more active by going for walks or taking up a hobby or getting involved in a sport.
- 6) Reduce meat products and reduce the intake of refined foods such as refined sugar and white breads. Eating fruits and vegetables is good for the mind, body and the environment.
- 7) Talk soft and less, avoid gossiping and criticizing others.
- 8) To consider that your body is simply the vehicle of your soul. Your body may not be a sleek "Porsche" but it does get you from A to B. Considering the self separate from the body will reduce the stress of being overweight and enable you to adopt a more positive outlook.
- 9) Remember you can do what ever you wish if you have a benevolent attitude.
- 10) Treat yourself regularly, have a massage, try yoga, meditation, aromatherapy or any alternative therapy.
- 11) If there has been an ongoing medical problem seek a second opinion from another Doctor or arrange a visit to a specialist.
- 12) Seek help with any mental problem that persists, visit a counselor, psychologist, hypnotherapist or ring a psychic.
- 13) Be positive, light and happy: think it and you will become.

Conclusion

In the end of this paper suggest that the Sports Person, Individuals and the society all have to relief from stress and achieve excellence in their own field through their Yoga Practice only. Yoga practice not only as a part of programme to reduce, Stress but also as a way to attaining other Goals.

Reference

- [1] Iyengar, B.K.S. (1968). Light on Yoga. London: George Allen and Unwin Ltd. Chandrasekar. k (2003). Yoga for Health, Delhi; Khel Sathiya Kendra.
- [2] Anatomy of Hatha Yoga- First Indian Edition-Delhi, 2004- H. David Coulter
- [3] The Yoga System of Health and Relief from Tesio (New York- Coror Stoe Litarary Publications, 1957)- Yogi Wittaldass.
- [4] Asana, International Yoga Journal- issue 133, Jan 2014 Manavalakai Yoga- Vethathiri Maharishi

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ROLE OF YOGA IN WOMEN'S MENTAL HEALTH & WELL-BEING

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Abstract

This article focuses on the importance of yoga women's mental health in well-beingness of our body. Yoga is the absolute best well-being and health module as it is extensive and all encompassing in nature. Wellness is a functioning course of becoming mindful of and settling on decisions toward a sound and satisfying life. Health is more than being liberated from disease; it is a unique process of progress and development. All kind of body wellbeing advances appropriate consideration of our bodies for ideal wellbeing and body work. There are many pieces of health that all should be really focused on together. In general, good health promotes a balanced view of physical activity, nutrition, and mental health to keep your body in good health and fitness. Currently yoga is being taken as a therapeutically agent for health. It not only prevents and cures the disease but also helps in maintenance of positive health. Yoga lays great emphasis on strengthening inherent defensive mechanisms of human body and mind rather than attaching and eradicating individual offending factor. It develops immunity and resistance in human body and helps the body and mind in attaining homeostatic balance. The strengthening of defense mechanism and harmony between mind and body prevents onset of disease. The aim of yoga therefore is also the attainment of physical, mental, social and spiritual health and well-being.

Keywords: *Yoga, Women, Vedas, Upanishads, Spiritual, Mental Health, Well-Being*

Introduction

Yoga is a powerful way of boosting the delight of living in a fit and sound body. Standard act of yoga can give greater adaptability, greater dependability, and give your body great equilibrium and strength. In today's fast-paced world and present corona virus disease [COVID]-19 condition, it is as important as ever to attend to your mind, body, and spirit. Yogic concepts aid in the strengthening and promote good health, enabling us to cope better with stress. Yoga is the science of living well, and as such, it is meant to be practiced on a regular basis. It affects the physical, vital, mental, emotional, psychic, and spiritual elements of a person. Mental disorders affect women and men differently. Common mental disorders like depression, anxiety and somatoform disorders are more prevalent among women than in men. Reproductive events influence the presentation of mental disorders. Women specially are vulnerable to mental health problems during pregnancy and postpartum periods due to biological and environmental changes occurring in these periods. In this article we explore the role of yoga in Premenstrual syndromes, prenatal mental health, chronic pain conditions in women and menopausal symptoms.

Yoga in Premenstrual syndromes

Many women experience physical and psychological symptoms before menstruation which is termed as premenstrual syndrome (PMS). Majority of women may experience one or two symptoms of mild severity but a small percentage of women experience the severe form known as premenstrual dysphoric disorder (PMDD).

Yoga in Perinatal Mental Health

Research shows that the rate of perinatal depression is estimated to be between 11% and 26%, with subclinical levels of depression affecting as many as 20% to 49% in this population. Suicide due to untreated depression can be a major cause of maternal mortality in the perinatal period. Depressed pregnant women experience higher rates of preeclampsia, spontaneous abortion, and pre-birth complications, and infants of depressed mothers are at higher risk of pre-term delivery and low birth weight.

Yoga in Chronic Pain Conditions

Chronic pain conditions are common in women and are associated with significant psychological distress. The available treatments often need long term use of medications with its associated side effects with partial or poor response to treatment.

Yoga in Treatment of Menopause Symptoms

Around 20% of patients suffer from severe menopausal symptoms while 60% suffer from mild symptoms. Menopausal symptoms include mood changes, bloating, aches and pains, headaches, hot flushes, night sweats, tiredness, insomnia, weight gain, depression, irritability, forgetfulness, lack of concentration, urinary frequency, vaginal dryness and sexual problems.

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Role of Yoga Maintaining Good Mental Health and Well-Being for Women

All-Round Fitness

You are truly healthy when you are not just physically fit but also mentally and emotionally balanced. As Sri Sri Ravi Shankarji puts it, —Health is not a mere absence of disease. It is a dynamic expression of life – in terms of how joyful, loving and enthusiastic you are. This is where yoga helps: postures, pranayama (breathing techniques) and meditation are a holistic fitness package.

Weight Loss

What many want! Yoga benefits here too. Sun Salutations and Kapal Bhati pranayama are some ways to help lose weight with yoga.

Stress Relief

A few minutes of yoga during the day can be a great way to get rid of stress that accumulates daily in both the body and mind. Yoga postures, pranayama and meditation are effective techniques to release stress.

Inner Peace.

We all love to visit peaceful, serene spots, rich in natural beauty. Little do we realize that peace can be found right within us and we can take a mini-vacation to experience this any time of the day! Benefit from a small holiday every day with yoga and meditation. Yoga is also one of the best ways to calm a disturbed mind.

Improved Immunity

Our system is a seamless blend of the body, mind and spirit. An irregularity in the body affects the mind and similarly unpleasantness or restlessness in the mind can manifest as an ailment in the body. Yoga poses massage organs and strengthens muscles; breathing techniques and meditation release stress and improve immunity.

Living with Greater Awareness

The mind is constantly involved in activity – swinging from the past to the future but never staying in the present. By simply being aware of this tendency of the mind, we can actually save ourselves from getting stressed or worked up and relax the mind.

Better Relationships

Yoga can even help improve your relationship with your spouse, parents, friends or loved ones! A mind that is relaxed, happy and contented is better able to deal with sensitive relationship matters

Increased Energy

Do you feel completely drained out by the end of the day? Shuttling between multiple tasks through the day can sometimes be quite exhausting. A few minutes of yoga everyday provide the secret to feeling fresh and energetic even after a long day.

Better Flexibility & Posture

You only need to include yoga in your daily routine to benefit from a body that is strong, supple and flexible.

Better Intuition

Yoga and meditation have the power to improve your intuitive ability so that you effortlessly realize what needs to be done, when and how, to yield positive results.

Powerful Lunge

Yoga activities specially concerned with pranayam help in the promotion and increase in strength and stamina of our lunge power in terms of their expansion and contraction enabling.

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Improve Respiratory Power

Yoga help us in regulating the respiration activities of our body adding efficiency to our respiratory power including increase in its amplitude stability and smoothness and decrease in the respiratory rate.

Healthy Muscles

These provide valuable help in the proper functioning and control over the movement of our muscles including the spinal cord. As a result we are able to maintain proper posture of our body including proper erectness of our spinal cord.

Purify Body

These help us in the tasks of the cleanliness and purification of the inner organs and systems of our body including the purification of our blood and its pathways, cleanliness of the respiratory and digestive systems and proper let out and excretion of the unwanted foreign material from our body .

Healthy Body

Yoga activities not only prove as strong deterrent for the prevention of the various ailments and diseases but also provide valuable solutions for their proper cure and treatment.

Powerful Mind

It is well said that there lies a healthy mind in a healthy body maintained through yogic activities. One can enjoy good mental health with a sound physical health obtained through yogic activities.

Control Over Mind.

Yoga sadhna provides the desired ability and strength for exercising desirable control over his senses, emotions and gratification of desires and fluctuations of the mind. Sustaining of attention and concentration acquired through such control and restrain then may provide a substantial ground of the development of intellectual powers.

Internal Purification

Yoga sadhna helps not only to have purification and cleanliness of the internal organs and Systems of our body but it also pays a lot of consideration for the purification of our inner self.

Self-Development

Yogic activities help the individual to imbibe the spirit of self-awareness, confidence in one's abilities and strengths, self-discipline and intrinsic motivation, self-acceptance and self actualization etc. for seeking his maximum self-development and enhancement.

Healthy Mind

Yogic activities help to free from any unusual anxiety, depression and fluctuation of mood or temperament.

Improvement of Mental Health and Wellness through Yoga

Disciplined Life

When one examines the lives of all outstanding individuals, one thing becomes clear: they are all disciplined. There are many things in today's living that cause you to become distracted from the important areas of life, obstructing your disciplined advancement. Yoga creates a positive nature of mind for well-beingness.

Inspire Happiness in Your Mind

As previously stated, yoga is popular over the world for its health benefits. It's crucial to remember, however, that health or good health extends beyond the physical body. It also relates to mental health. No matter how powerful a person's body is, if his or her mind is not in good shape, he or she will not be able to progress. Yoga also gives the mind that peace, making a person feel eternally encouraged to take on any challenge in life.

Create Positive Nature

For someone who is happy on the inside, a problem is meaningless. As a result, maybe the most important advantage of yoga is that it makes people happier. Yoga helps the body achieve extraordinary hormonal balance.

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Increase Immunity Power

There is no workout in the world in the present condition of COVID-19, aside from yoga, which makes the person immune from the inside out. This is, without a doubt, the greatest blessing a person can receive. Yoga is a confidence builder in today's disorderly lifestyle and COVID-19, where threats of being attacked by microbes or becoming sick are always there. As a result, it is recommended that you practice yoga on a daily basis to give your body the best present possible.

Increase Fitness Level

Among the most obvious benefits of yoga is increased flexibility, but it can also lead to a variety of other advantages, such as a reduction in aches and pains. Tight hips can affect the alignment of the thigh and shin bones, causing knee pain knees. Tight hamstrings can cause back pain by flattening the lower spine. Many yoga asana also improve muscle strength.

Yoga for Mindfulness, Stress Relief, and Mental Health

Hatha yoga uses gentle and slower moving forms, incorporating a variety of poses that are ideal for beginners and for those who are drawn to yoga for stress relief, relaxation, enhanced mindfulness, and enhanced mental health benefits.

Yoga for Spiritual Well-Being

Even though most individuals (both students and teachers) initiate yoga practice primarily for exercise and stress relief, it is worth noting that most continue their practice for its spiritual Benefits – regardless of the style of yoga.

Conclusion

Yoga is the original mind body medicine and is one of the greatest treasures of the unique Indian cultural heritage. As both an art and science it has a lot to offer humankind in terms of an understanding of both the human mind as well as all aspects of our multilayered existence. Yogic lifestyle, Yogic diet, Yogic attitudes and various Yogic practices help man to strengthen himself and develop positive health thus enabling him to withstand stress better. Yoga is truly a wholesome and integral science of life that deals with multidimensional aspects of health in both the individual and society.

References

- [1] Brown, R. P., & Gerbarg, P. L. (2005). Sudarshan Kriya yogic breathing in the treatment of stress, anxiety, and depression: part I—neurophysiologic model. *Journal of Alternative & Complementary Medicine*, 11(1), 189-201.
- [2] Cramer, H., Lauche, R., Langhorst, J., & Dobos, G. (2012). Effectiveness of yoga for menopausal symptoms: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2012.
- [3] Giambrone, C. A. (2019). Let Them See You Sweat: Integrating Yoga and Well-Being. In *Psychology of Health-Biopsychosocial Approach*. IntechOpen.
- [4] Sheffield, K. M., & Woods-Giscombé, C. L. (2016). Efficacy, feasibility, and acceptability of perinatal yoga on women's mental health and well-being: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Holistic Nursing*, 34(1), 64-79.
- [6] Tsai, S. Y. (2016). Effect of yoga exercise on premenstrual symptoms among female employees in Taiwan. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 13(7), 721.

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION - NEED AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Inclusive Education (IE) is a new loom towards educating the children with special needs with normal students within the same regular class room. The aim of Inclusive Education is all children with disabilities including 'those who have physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and efficient participation in society on an equal basis with others. In India out of the 121crores population, 2.68 crores persons are disabled which is 2.21% of the total population. In 2011, around 7.62 percent of India's population with disability was children (Census of India). There are an estimated 8 million children out of school in India (MHRD 2009 statistics), many of them are marginalised by dimensions such as poverty, gender, disability, and caste This article thoroughly analyses the need of Inclusive Education and challenges faced in Inclusive Education. This article focuses on how children with disabilities meet their challenging needs in inclusive setups. This review is made after exploring and comparing survey and research data from authentic sources like UNESCO, UNICEF, journals, etc.

Introduction

Every child has the right to education. The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) recognises the right to inclusive education for all persons with disabilities. Rousseau has rightly pointed out that due to varied circumstances and privileges, children shows differences in their performance and achievement. It is therefore, imperative to provide adequate facilities to children to develop their abilities to the optimum. Equality of educational opportunity is essential to achieve this purpose. Inclusive education is an approach to educating the students with special needs with non-special needs students. The main principle of Inclusive Education is access and quality education. Inclusive Education is defined as a process of addressing the diverse needs of all learners by reducing barriers to and within the learning environment. It means attending the age-appropriate class of the child's local school, with individually tailored support (UNICEF 2007).

Definition of Inclusion

According UNESCO views inclusion as 'a dynamic approach of responding positively to pupils diversity and of seeing individual differences not as problems, but as opportunities for enriching learning.' Inclusive education – also called inclusion – is education that includes everyone, with non- disabled and Disabled people (including those with "special educational needs") learning together in mainstream schools, colleges and universities.

Need and Importance of Inclusive Education

Exclusion is the main cause for the importance of inclusion. Students with disabilities are denied access to education should be included in inclusive education irrespective of their strengths and weakness. The Chapter V of the Person with Disability Act confirms that every child with disability is entitled to a free education up to the age of 18 years. In this view , the Government of India had accelerated the new approach of Inclusive Education to achieve the target of Education to All (EFA 2010). 78% of Indian population lives in rural areas without provision for special schools. Thus, the inclusive Education is important and it is needed to be introduced in Government and Private Schools in rural areas. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) was launched to achieve the goal of Universalisation of Elementary Education in 2001 is one such initiative. A zero rejection policy had implemented under SSA, to safeguard the children with Special Needs irrespective of the disabilities, to provide the quality and meaningful education. Family involvement and support for inclusion is very essential component for educating the child. Participation of family members in School and class room activities enables the child nurturing with disabilities. The diverse needs of Children with disabilities and the quest to make Schools more learning friendly requires regular and special education teachers to consult and collaboration with one another as well as family and community to develop effective strategies teaching and learning within inclusive setups. (Jelas, 2010). Inclusive Education is best way to help children with disabilities to succeed. Researcher shown that children do better academic performance in inclusive setting provides opportunities to develop relationships. Peer Tutoring, friendship, socialization , personal principles, comfort level for CWSN and caring class room environment are benefits of Inclusive Education.

Inclusive Education in India

The Government of India had created various policies for integrated education, In 1964, Kothari

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commission was introduced to improve the education system including people with disabilities. The Integrated Child Development Scheme (ICDS) 1974 (NCERT, 2011) was created by Ministry of Human Resource Development to reach out 'vulnerable populations' to provide services for early intervention, including nutrition, health care and pre-school facilities for children of 0- 5 years old. In India, National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) joined hands with UNICEF and launched Project Integrated Education for Disabled Children (PIED) in the year 1987, to strengthen the integration of learners with disabilities into regular Schools. The concept of Inclusive Education has been encompass not only students with disabilities, but also all students who may be disadvantaged. This paved the way for developing the National Curriculum Framework (NCF-2005) it gives emphasis of including and retaining all children in school through a programme that reaffirms the value of each child. IEDC was revised and named "Inclusive Education of the Disabled at the Secondary Stage (IEDSS) in 2009-10 to provide assistance for the inclusive education of the disabled children at 9th and 10th classes. This scheme subsumed under Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA) from 2013. It is important to integrate these children into regular schools to help them socialise and build their confidence. The Rehabilitation Council of India (RCI) is registered society in 1986 mainly responsible for education and rehabilitation of Children with special needs.

Barriers to Inclusive Education

As a coin has two sides, Inclusive Education also has positive and negative impacts. The major section of the disabled population made some effort to cope with the new normal. There are numerous benefits to all students, both disabled and non-disabled. In spite of benefits many barriers to the implementation of Inclusive Education. A UNESCO article Outlined the barriers such as Physical, Attitudinal and Instructional.

Physical Barriers

Students with Physical disabilities are expected to attend Schools that are inaccessible to them. In rural areas, the schools are poorly cared buildings which are restrict accessibility for CWSN. Environmental barriers can include doors, stairs, ramps, passageways and recreational areas.

Attitudinal Barriers

Societal norms are the biggest barrier to inclusion. Prejudices against those with differences can lead to discrimination, which inhibits the educational process. The challenges of inclusive education might be blamed on the students challenges instead of the shortcomings of the educational system.

Instructional Barriers

Curriculum: A rigid curriculum does not allow for experimentation or the use of different teaching methods can be an enormous barrier to inclusion. Study plans don't recognize different styles of learning hinder the school experience for all students, even though not traditionally recognised as having physical or mental challenges. Teachers: Untrained Teachers who are unwilling or unenthusiastic in working with disabled students are a drawback to successful inclusion. The Teachers under large workloads may resent the added duties of coming up with different approaches for the same lessons. Language and communication Barriers: Students are expected to learn in a language that is new to them is obviously a significant barrier to successful learning. These students face discrimination and low expectations.

Challenges in Inclusive Education

UNICEF's Report on the status of Disability in India 2000 states that there are around 30 million children in India suffering from some form of disability. The sixth All India Educational Survey (NCERT, 1998) reports that out of India's 200 million school aged children (6- 14years), 20 million requires special need education. According to Barton, (1997), " Inclusive Education is not merely about providing access into mainstream school for pupils who have previously been excluded. Inclusive Education is about the participation of All children and young people and the removal of all forms of exclusionary practice.' However, a wide gap in policy and practice exists in the country with respect to Inclusive education. There are number of challenges that hinder proper practice of Inclusive Education in our country. some of the challenges are:

Attitude towards inclusive education and disability : Attitude among teachers, parents , peers , administrators and policy planners towards inclusion and disability requires positive attitude. Negative attitudes are still persisting among in many of them is adversely affecting inclusive education scenario in India. Teachers in mainstream schools were less positive about the potential of children with disabilities than special school teachers. A number of studies found that general education teachers are not supportive of inclusion. Teachers with negative attitudes believe that inclusion is a burden on teachers and they should receive special service delivery in special education settings to avoid negative impacts with peers in regular classroom. Skills of Teachers in Inclusive Education: Skills of Teachers are essential for successful implementation of inclusive education in primary and secondary schools. 70% of the regular school teachers

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had neither received training in special education nor had any experience in teaching with disabilities. 87% of the teachers did not have access to support services in their classrooms. The inefficiency of teachers to develop and use instructional materials for inclusion students. It is a huge challenge faced in inclusive education. (Chaote, J.S. (1997)

Improper Curriculum adaptation; Curriculum adaptations suited to special and unique needs of every learner, including children with disabilities are necessary. Concepts like 'Universal Instructional Design' are to be properly developed and incorporated into the curriculum. curricular adaptations are missing or improper. **School Environment:** School Environment including difficulties in physical access needs accommodations for practicing inclusive Education. However, such accommodations are not there in majority of the .Schools .Special facilities like ramps, lifts, handrails, modified toilets for PWD and directional cues etc are not available in Schools. **Support services:** Effective support services needed for the children with disabilities like various therapies. For implementing inclusive Education in all educational institutions, at all levels, need strong support services. But existing support services are inadequate and insufficient. **Family collaboration:** Family has a very important role in implementing inclusive education in India, Family is main responsibility in the development of the children with special needs. The nature of the Indian society and culture, family is foremost role to play in nurturing the children with special needs. **ICT availability:** Information and Communication Technology is helps all human beings including special need children in education and training. There are many pedagogical and assistive devices that are available and it is particularly useful for children with disabilities. Present age is the age of information and communication technology which should be available in the inclusive education.

Conclusions

The Government of India needs to bridge the gaps in their education system to build a strong system of inclusive education in the country. So, there are some suggestions for better implementation of Inclusive Education; Regular School Teachers should be trained both in General and Special education. Teachers attitude towards Inclusion and disability should be changed. Trained Special Educators should be appointed in Inclusive Schools as a Resource Teachers with appropriate Resource room settings to train children with Special needs. Inclusive education system should be flexible. Teaching methods and materials should be flexible used to give these children the widest possible access to the regular curriculum. Physical barriers such as School environment - building , ramps, lifts sign boards, handrails, adapted toilets should be provided for all Government and Private schools. Teacher education curriculum has to develop a "whole faculty approach" in facilitating an inclusive pre-service teacher education curriculum embedded across all discipline areas. Expenses involved in the set-up of Inclusive Schools are huge and requires lot of financial support. But the Government does not willing to incur this huge expenditure. Hence the Government had to take necessary steps to modify the Schools into barrier free. Parents have a right to be involved in all decision-making concerning their child. They should be seen as partners in the education process.

References

- [1] Chaote, J.S. (1997), Successful Inclusive Teaching. Allyn and Bacon.
- [2] Dr.K.S. RamaKrishnan , Dr. D. Vinodh Kumar and Dr. P. Rajasekaran (2014) Education in the Emerging Indian /society, Sri Ram Printing , Chennai.
- [3] <https://enabled.in/wp/disabled-population-in-india-as-per-census-2011-2016-updated>
[https://www.educationforallindia.com/statistics-of-school-education-2009-10%20\(MHRD\)](https://www.educationforallindia.com/statistics-of-school-education-2009-10%20(MHRD))
- [4] Inclusive Education (2021) School of Special Education & Rehabilitation, Tamil Nadu Open Universtiy, Chennai.
- [5] Kumar Sanjeev Ph.D & Khagendra Kumar Ph.D.(2007) Inclusive Education in India, Department of Education Patna University, Bihar (INDIA) Electronic Journal of Inclusive Education, Vol.2, No.2.
- [6] Ministry of Human Resource Development. National Policy on Education (PoA-1992). New Delhi: Government of India.
- [7] Nurul Aina Zakaria, (2017) The effects of inclusive education on the Self-concept of students with special educational needs, National University of Malaysia,
- [8] UNICEF for every child(2017) Inclusive education- Understanding Article 24 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

MOTTO AND PRINCIPLES OF HOLISTIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

Holistic education is a comprehensive approach to teaching where educators seek to address the emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in an integrated learning format. Emphasis is placed on positive school environments and providing whole-child supports to students. The goal of holistic education is to cultivate a developing child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual attributes. Serving the whole child means providing opportunities that are personalized to a child's skills and feelings. Ultimacy, also called enlightenment or union with cosmic harmony, is a common theme throughout the holistic literature. It is the highest potential of the student who is involved in a holistic educational process (Nielse2008). Students are empowered to improve their educational outcomes and gain the life skills necessary to take on a successful professional career. A society where we live in peace with our environment is what holistic education aims to build. The dominating way of being in contemporary society, consumerism, is rejected. It seeks an education that is based on the core truths of nature and the universe instead. The mission of holistic approach is to link the individual parts to the whole.

Keywords: *Holistic Education, Advantages, Principles, Wholeness*

Introduction

Education has to play a major role in ensuring the successful of the development. During the period extending from the past to the present day, economists, social scientists, and politicians have suggested that education has a crucial role in the development of a country. Holistic education places an emphasis on the whole growth of a learner instead of emphasizing only specific parts of the human experience. In addition to encouraging development in all spheres of human experience-intellectual, emotional, social, and so forth-it deemphasizes materialism. Holistic education proponents contend that it fosters harmonious interactions not only among individuals but also between those individuals and their surroundings. The advantages of holistic education are to improve the academic achievement, problem solving ability, enhanced mental and emotional well-being etc.

Holistic Education

A holistic approach to education aims to meet students' needs on all levels, including academically, socially, morally, and emotionally. Positive school climates and offering children whole-child supports-also referred to as wraparound supports-that address both academic and non-academic needs-are prioritised. Students are frequently assigned projects by teachers that require them to use their abilities for critical thinking to overcome issues in the real world.

Aim of Holistic Education

The goal of holistic education is to cultivate a developing child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual attributes. Giving chances that are tailored to a child's abilities and feelings is serving them as a whole. Lessons are delivered in a secure, encouraging setting that encourages pupils to play to their unique abilities. Teachers must be equipped to support pupils with a range of educational backgrounds and cognitive capacities. While a single overall principle informs holistic education, teachers may use a variety of techniques to foster a culture of holistic learning.

Scott Forbes (2003), proposed that "the goal of holistic education is best encapsulated by the term 'Ultimacy.'" He defined ultimacy as, (1) the highest state of being that a human can aspire to, either as a stage of development (e.g. enlightenment), as a moment of life that is the greatest but only rarely experienced by anyone (e.g. grace), or as a phase of life that is common in the population but usually rare in any particular individual's life (e.g., Maslow's peak-experience); and (2) a concern or engagement that is the greatest that a person can aspire to (e.g., being in service to something sacred). These two meanings can overlap or intertwine. Ultimacy, also called enlightenment or union with cosmic harmony, is a common theme throughout the holistic literature. It is the highest potential of the student who is involved in a holistic educational process (Nielse2008). The notions of Ultimacy lead holistic educators to their views of human nature and meaningful living. Holistic educators claim their view of original goodness stands in opposition to that of original sin, and that different view concerning the need (or lack of need) to control and shape children necessarily follow. Hence, holistic educators feel they have a different view of development which holds that people will naturally go towards the good, and that progress consists largely of unfolding, uncovering, or discovering what is natural or inherent in the child.

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Benefits of Holistic Education

Holistic education is based on a learning philosophy that brings a number of benefits to students, teachers, schools, and communities. Students are empowered to improve their educational outcomes and gain the life skills necessary to take on a successful professional career.

Improved Academic Achievement: Holistic education can improve the academic achievements of all children, regardless of background and circumstances, by catering to individual learning styles and providing a supportive learning environment. Children's brain capacities are increased when they feel physically and emotionally safe and connected to others, according to the Learning Policy Institute.

Enhanced Mental and Emotional Well-Being: In a supportive environment, where social and emotional learning is emphasized along with academics, students have a better chance of emerging with self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of social responsibility.

Increased Problem-Solving Ability: Students who are tasked with solving real-world problems that exist in their communities emerge with strong critical-thinking skills. These hands-on projects give students skills that will apply to their adult careers, such as how to gather, analyze, and report data and how to collaborate with others.

Reduced Impact of Inequities: By emphasizing integrated learning concepts, the whole-child approach to education has been shown to reduce the psychological impact of issues such as violence, abuse, or poverty on academic achievement, according to the Learning Policy Institute.

Four 'Pillars of Learning' in Holistic Education:

For methodological purpose only, holistic education has noted four pillars of learning in the twenty-first century. UNESCO has also indicated these same four pillars, although with slight differences. (Nava2001)

- 1) Learning to Learn
- 2) Learning to Do
- 3) Learning to Leave Together
- 4) Learning to Be

Basic Principles of Holistic Education

John Miller synthesizes holistic education as an approach that encompasses three main principles:

1) "Connection" – entails integrating school subjects; establishing connections with the community; fostering student's relationship with the earth; and encouraging students to connect to their souls, their deeper sense of selves.

2) "Inclusion" – refers to including students of diverse races and abilities and providing a range of educational approaches to attend the differences in learning styles.

3) "Balance" – means reaching for equilibrium between complementary energies (individual learning and group learning, analytic thinking and intuitive thinking, content and process, and learning and assessment).

Development of Human Education:

The primary purpose of education is to nourish the inherent possibilities of human development. Schools must be places that facilitate the whole development of all learners. Learning must be the deepening of relationships to self, to family and community members, to the global community, to the planet, and to the cosmos.

Honouring Individual Students:

Each learner is unique, inherently creative, with individual needs and abilities. This means welcoming personal differences and fostering in each student a sense of tolerance, respect, and appreciation for human diversity. Each individual is inherently creative, has unique physical, emotional, intellectual, and spiritual needs and abilities, and possesses an unlimited capacity to learn.

The Main Role of Experience:

Experience is dynamic and ever growing. The goal of education must be to nurture natural, healthy growth through experience, and not to present a limited, fragmented, pre-digested "curriculum" as the path to knowledge and wisdom.

New Role of Educators:

Holistic educators hold, rather, that educators ought to be facilitators of learning, which is an organic, natural process and not a product that can be turned out on demand. Teachers require the autonomy to design and implement learning environments that are appropriate to the needs of their particular students.

Freedom of Choice:

Students and parents should have opportunities for real choice at every stage of the learning process. Genuine education can only take place in an atmosphere of freedom. Freedom of inquiry, of expression, and of personal growth is all required.

Educating for Global Citizenship:

Each individual is a global citizen. Education therefore, should be an appreciation for the magnificent

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diversity of human experience. Human experience is vastly wider than any single culture's values or ways of thinking. In the emerging global community, we are being brought into contact with diverse cultures and worldviews as never before in history, Holistic educators believe that it is time for education to nurture an appreciation for the magnificent diversity of human experience and for the lost or still uncharted potentials within all human beings.

Educating for Earth Literacy:

Education must spring organically from a profound reverence for life in all its forms and nurture a relationship between humans and the natural world. We must rekindle a relationship between the human and the natural world that is nurturing, not exploitive. This is at the very core of our vision for the twenty-first century.

Spirituality and Education:

Holistic educators believe that all people are spiritual beings in human form who express their individuality through their talents, abilities, intuition, and intelligence. Just as the individual develops physically, emotionally, and intellectually, each person also develops spiritually. Spiritual experience and development manifest as a deep connection to self and others, a sense of meaning and purpose in daily life, an experience of the wholeness and interdependence of life, a respite from the frenetic activity, pressure and over-simulation of contemporary life, the fullness of creative experience, and a profound respect for the numinous mystery of life.

Conclusion

A holistic education trains future citizens who will offer a concern and mindfulness for others, for their communities, and for the world. It can be a source of fulfillment and enjoyment for instructors. It is compatible with both global education and environmental education, which are also based on the principles of interdependence and connectedness. Based on this interdependent perspective, holistic education seeks to create a society where we live in harmony with the surrounding environment. It rejects consumerism as the dominant mode of being in modern society. Instead, it seeks an education that is rooted in the fundamental realities of nature and existence. We have tended in education to forget the larger vision of wholeness and connectedness, and holistic education calls on us to restore that vision. Such a vision, of course, is a primary goal of Education for Sustainability.

References

- [1] School of Education Online (2020, May 14). American University. What is Holistic Education? Understanding the Benefits
- [2] Mahmoudi, S., Jafari, E., Nasrabadi, H., & Liaghatdar, M. (2012). Holistic Education: An Approach for 21 Century | Mahmoudi | International Education Studies <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ies/article/view/17024>
- [3] Grimes, B. (2007). Multidimensional classroom: development a comprehensive research base for Holistic education. Dissertation, England: University of Cambridge.
- [4] Hare, J. (2006). Toward an understanding of holistic education in the middle years of education. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 5(3), 23-25. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1475240906069453>
- [5] Forbes, S. (2003). Holistic education: An analysis of its ideas in nature. Brandon, VT: Foundation for Educational Renewal.
- [6] Flake, C. L. (2000). Holistic education: Principles, perspectives and practice. Brandon, VT: Holistic Education Press.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

REGULAR EXERCISES PROMOTING PHYSICAL FITNESS

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Introduction

Physical Fitness

Physical fitness is a state of health and well-being and, more specifically, the ability to perform aspects of sport, occupations and daily activities. Physical fitness is generally achieved through proper nutrition, moderate-vigorous physical exercises, and sufficient rest along with a formal recovery plan.

Regular Exercises

Regular physical activity is one of the most important things you can do for your health. Being physically active can improve your brain health, help manage weight, reduce the risk of disease, strengthen bones and muscles, and improve your ability to do everyday activities.

Endurance, or Aerobic

Keep your heart, lungs, and circulatory system healthy and improve your overall fitness. Examples include brisk walking, jogging, swimming, and biking.

Strength, or Resistance Training

Exercises make your muscles stronger. Some examples are lifting weights and using a resistance band.

Balance

Exercises can make it easier to walk on uneven surfaces and help prevent falls. To improve your balance, try tai chi or exercises like standing on one leg.

Flexibility

Exercises stretch your muscles and can help your body stay limber. Yoga and doing various stretches can make you more flexible.

Health Benefits of Exercise Regular Exercise and Physical Activity May

Help you control your weight : Along with diet, exercise plays an important role in controlling your weight and preventing obesity. To maintain your weight, the calories you eat and drink must equal the energy you burn. To lose weight, you must use more calories than you eat and drink.

Reduce Your Risk of Heart Diseases

Exercise strengthens your heart and improves your circulation. The increased blood flow raises the oxygen levels in your body. This helps lower your risk of heart diseases such as high cholesterol, coronary artery disease, and heart attack. Regular exercise can also lower your blood pressure and triglyceride levels.

Help Your Body Manage Blood Sugar and Insulin Levels

Exercise can lower your blood sugar level and help your insulin work better. This can cut down your risk for metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes. And if you already have one of those diseases, exercise can help you to manage it.

Help You Quit Smoking

Exercise may make it easier to quit smoking by reducing your cravings and withdrawal symptoms. It can also help limit the weight you might gain when you stop smoking.

Improve your mental health and mood:

During exercise, your body releases chemicals that can improve your mood and make you feel more relaxed. This can help you deal with stress and reduce your risk of depression.

Promoting Physical Activity as a Way of Life

As a parent, you need to encourage healthy habits—including exercise—in your youngsters. Physical activity should become as routine a part of their lives as eating and sleeping. Reassure them that sports such as

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cycling (always with a helmet), swimming, basketball, jogging, walking briskly, cross country skiing, dancing, aerobics, and soccer, played regularly, are not only fun but can promote health. Some sports, like baseball, that require only sporadic activity are beneficial in a number of ways, but they do not promote fitness. Physical activity can be healthful in the following ways:

Improve Large Muscle Strength and Endurance

As your child's muscles become stronger, he will be able to exercise for longer periods of time, as well as protect himself from injuries—strong muscles provide better support for the joints.

Increase Flexibility

For complete physical fitness, children need to be able to twist and bend their bodies through the full range of normal motions without overexerting themselves or causing injury. When children are flexible like this, they are more agile.

Maintain Proper Weight

Twelve percent of children in the pre-puberty years are overweight, but few of these youngsters are physically active. Exercise can effectively burn calories and fat and reduce appetite.

Reduce Stress. Unmanaged stress can cause muscle tightness, which can contribute to headaches, stomach aches, and other types of discomfort. Your child needs to learn not only to recognize stress in his body but also to diffuse it effectively.

Make Exercise a part of my Regular Routine

Make Everyday Activities more Active

Even small changes can help. You can take the stairs instead of the elevator. Walk down the hall to a co-worker's office instead of sending an email. Wash the car yourself. Park further away from your destination.

Be active with friends and family

Having a workout partner may make you more likely to enjoy exercise. You can also plan social activities that involve exercise. You might also consider joining an exercise group or class, such as a dance class, hiking club, or volleyball team.

Keep Track of your Progress

Keeping a log of your activity or using a fitness tracker may help you set goals and stay motivated.

Make exercise more fun

Try listening to music or watching TV while you exercise. Also, mix things up a little bit - if you stick with just one type of exercise, you might get bored. Try doing a combination of activities.

Find activities that you can do even when the weather is bad

You can walk in a mall, climb stairs, or work out in a gym even if the weather stops you from exercising outside.

References

- [1] Caring for Your School-Age Child: Ages 5 to 12 (Copyright © 2004 American Academy of Pediatrics) The information contained on this Web site should not be used as a substitute for the medical care and advice of your pediatrician. 8600 Rockville Pike, Bethesda, MD 20894 U.S. Department of Health and Human Services National Institutes of Health Last updated May 8, 2020.

HOLISTIC OUTCOME BASED AND MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION

DIGITAL PORTFOLIO, INFOGRAPHIC AND BLENDED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AMONG THE TERTIARY LEVEL SCIENCE TEACHERS

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Abstract

The present investigation attempts to find out the relationship among the digital portfolio Infographic and Blended learning environment among the tertiary level science teachers. For which, a normative survey method was used as a method of the study. The 250 science faculties constitute the sample of the study and they were administered the tool that correlatively collect their use of digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment. The results arrived through statistical calculation shown that there exist significant relationship among the tertiary level science teachers' digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment. The categorical variables wise analysis also revealed that there exist significant relationships among the tertiary level science teachers' digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment. Hence, it is sensitized that the digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment are hand to hand in term of their components and skills. Thus, an insight is gained as an implication that once the digital portfolio, infographic are enhanced among the teachers, their blended learning environment will also be good.

Keywords: *Arts and Science Colleges, Blended Learning Environment, Digital Portfolio, Infographic.*

Introduction

The advent of Information and communication technology (ICT) has brought a sea change in the process of teaching and learning. Teaching methods and learning strategies have changed and learning has become learner-centred through technological devices. Info graphic helps teachers to make use of blended learning environment. Students can learn through classroom teaching as well as online wherever it is possible and feasible. Infographic helps teachers to create digital portfolio and use it to teach in blended learning environment. Difficult concepts are made into easy learning modules with the help of digital portfolios using infographics. Presentation of difficult complex concepts in science through digital portfolios make teaching more feasible and learning becomes easier for students. To prepare digital portfolios teachers must update their knowledge in information and communication technology. It is possible for teachers to collect content information and store in digital portfolio using infographic. The use of digital portfolios sustains the interest of students and their active participation in learning can also be ensured. The strategy of using graphics further enhances interactive learning, students discussing with teachers and peers. Studies have shown that blended learning helps reducing drop outs in tertiary education. Infographic, digital portfolio and blended learning are especially more helpful in teaching and learning of science.

Need for the Study

In the era of information technology every activity in human life is accomplished in digital mode from purchasing merchandise to launching of satellite. In this context education is also influenced by technological devices. The explosion of knowledge necessitated that the process of teaching and learning must also change. Now teaching is learner-centred and learning takes place beyond the classroom. Students learn both online and offline. Time spent for learning and resources available have changed the paradigm for teaching and learning. It is less time and more content and can learn whenever and wherever possible is the dictum. In blended learning digital portfolios are designed with infographics and complex concepts are made simple for better learning. Teachers need to have knowledge of technology, expertise in using graphics to prepare digital portfolios and be proficient in subject content. Digital portfolios are more useful in teaching science subjects. If teachers can make use of graphics and present complex concepts in portfolios to the students, meaningful teaching and successful learning can be ensured. Based on this exigency, it is necessary to determine the relationships between infographic, digital portfolio and blended learning environment in their application among tertiary level science teachers.

Assumptions

It is assumed that there is no significant relationship between the digital portfolio Infographic and blended learning environment of the Science faculty members who are working at Arts and Science Colleges. It is assumed that the demographic variables have no influence in the relationship of digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment among the science faculty members.

Statement of the Problem

The present investigation aims to study the relationship of digital portfolio Infographic and

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Blended learning environment that using by the Science faculty members of the Arts and Science Colleges.

Objectives

- 1) To study the relationship between digital portfolio, Infographic and Blended learning environment of science faculty members working in Arts and Science Colleges.
- 2) To study the above stated objective based on the selected demographic variables Such as Gender, Locality of Institutions, Types of Institutions and Years of Experience

Hypotheses

- 1) There exist significant relationship between the Digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment among the Science faculty members.
- 2) There exist significant relationships between the Digital portfolios, Infographic among the Science faculty members in relation to the demographic variables.

Methodology

The researcher adopted the normative survey method for this investigation. Data was collected from 250 faculty members who are working at Arts and Science Colleges. For this study, the investigator used the Simple random sampling Technique. A scale that measures the Digital portfolio, Infographic and Blended learning environment among the science faculty members who are working at Arts and Science Colleges were established and validated by the investigators and administered to the selected sample.

Results and Discussion

S.No	Variable	Sub variable	N	Digital portfolio vs. Infographic	Level of significance	Digital portfolio vs. Blended learning environment	Level of significance	Infographic vs. Blended learning environment	Level of significance
1.	Gender	Male	128	0.70	NS	0.79	NS	0.68	NS
		Female	122	0.42	NS	0.58	NS	0.64	NS
2.	Locality of Institutions	Rural	137	0.61	NS	0.70	NS	0.69	NS
		Urban	113	0.553	NS	0.73	NS	0.62	NS
3.	Type of Institutions	Government	118	0.63	NS	0.77	NS	0.71	NS
		Private	132	0.56	NS	0.65	NS	0.62	NS
4.	Years of experience	Below 3years	79	0.69	NS	0.80	NS	0.70	NS
		3-5 years	64	0.49	NS	0.61	NS	0.53	NS

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		5-10years	56	0.44	NS	0.49	NS	0.58	NS
		Above 10 years	51	0.56	NS	0.77	NS	0.76	NS

Hypothesis

There exists significant relationship between the Digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment among the Science faculty members.

Relationship among the Digital portfolio, infographic and blended learning environment among the Science faculty members.

Variable	N	Correlation value	Level of significance
Digital portfolio Vs Infographic	250	0.588	NS
Digital portfolio Vs Blended Learning Environment		0.713	NS
Infographic Vs Blended Learning Environment		0.663	NS

(Significant @ 0.05 level)

From the above correlation table, it is understood that there exists no significant relationship between the Digital portfolio vs. Infographic and Digital portfolio vs. Blended Learning Environment and Infographic vs. Blended Learning Environment.

Hypothesis

There exist significant relationships between the Digital portfolio, Infographic and Blended Learning Environment among the Science faculty members in relation to the demographic variables.

Relationships between the Digital portfolio, Infographic and Blended Learning Environment among the Science faculty members in relation to the demographic variables. From the above correlation table, it is understood that there exists no significant relationship between the Digital portfolio vs. Infographic and Digital portfolio vs. Blended Learning Environment and Infographic vs. Blended Learning Environment among the Science faculty members in relation to the variables such as Gender, Locality on colleges institutions, Types of Institutions and Years of Experience.

Educational Implications

The findings revealed that there exists significant relationship between Digital portfolio vs. Infographic and Digital portfolio vs. Blended Learning Environment and Infographic vs. Blended Learning Environment among the Science faculty members. This is an indication that the teachers are good at using digital portfolio, infographic and their blended learning environment. These results indicated that the both avenues can be taken in to the greater height among the science faculty members by providing adequate training programmes. The teachers may be interviewed to taken up the usage of both digital portfolio, infographic and utilize blended learning environment of the maths faculty members by administering the training, programmes, workshops and necessary plans.

References

- [1] Abrami, P., Venkatesh, V., Elizabeth, M. and Wade, C. A. (2013). Using Electronic Portfolios to Foster Literacy and Self-Regulated Learning Skills in Elementary Students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(4).
- [2] Aguiar, E., Chawla, N.V., Brockman, J., Ambrose, G.A. and Goodrich, V. (2014). Engagement vs Performance: Using Electronic Portfolio to predict First Semester Engineering Student Retention. *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Learning Analytics and Knowledge*. 103 - 112.
- [3] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2019). Teachers self-efficacy scale: development and validation. *Review of Research*, 8(6), 1-8.

ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF NON-TRIBAL HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Indian government has introduced a number of schemes to improve the educational status of school students, yet the efforts have not been yielded desired results. The study's main goal was to find out the achievement motivation of non-tribal high school students in Namakkal district. The sample consists of 250 students. With this objective in view, a sample was taken from the government schools, government Aided schools and private schools by using random sampling technique. To measure the Achievement motivation of non-tribal students the researcher used modified tool of Deo-Mohan Achievement Motivation (n-Ah) Scale and the reliability of the tool was checked by test and retest method. The data were analyzed using the 't'-test, ANOVA, standard deviation (SD), and mean (X). This study shows some school pupils have less Achievement Motivation. So, it is clear that special attention should be given to the students about the need and importance of education to improve their role and responsibility in the society.

Keywords: Achievement, Motivation, Non-Tribal Students.

Introduction

Education is the balanced growth of a person's physical, social, intellectual, artistic, and spiritual faculties. Experience produces education. It is the method and means through which the information, abilities, and attitudes of the race are communicated to the community's members. The process of assisting a youngster in adjusting to a changing reality is known as education. A student who strives for education is prepared, among other things, to fulfil his potential as a citizen of his country.

Achievement Motivation

The term motivation refers to the arousal of a tendency to act to produce one or more effects, i.e., to achieve any desired thing. In the words of McClelland et al., (1953), "An achievement motivated individual is likely to exhibit self-assurance, positive outlook pragmatism, hope and faith in a bright future, while an individual lacking in Achievement Motivation would exhibit all-round pessimism, distrust and despair"(Pp.210-218)

i) David McClelland's Need for Achievement

David McClelland et al., (1953) wrote a book titled, "The Achieving Society. They did a lot of researches on Achievement Motivation (Need for Achievement /n-Ach). It is an attempt to categorize societies as achieving and non-Achieving ones. According to them, "when children are urged to perform as best as they could for the sheer joy of performance in any worthwhile area of human endeavour, they are amazed at their own potentialities".

ii) David Ausubel's Perception of Achievement Motivation

David Ausubel, the profounder of Meaningful Reception Learning and Expository Teaching, perceives three components of achievement motivation. These are

- 1) Cognitive Urge, Which is task oriented. The individual attempts to satisfy his need to know and understand. The reward of discovering new knowledge resides in carrying out of the task
- 2) Self-enhancement, which is ego-oriented, represents a desire for increased 'Prestige and Status' gained by doing well scholastically or otherwise. It deals to feelings of adequacy and self-esteem.
- 3) Affiliation, which is dependent of others for approval. Satisfaction comes from such approval irrespective of the case, so that the individual uses academic success simply as a means of recognition by those on whom he depends for assurance.

Non-Tribal Students

The students belonging to OC, BC, MBC and SC communities are called as non-tribal students. Here the investigator conducted his study among non-tribal students and also conducted another study with tribal students.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find the level of achievement motivation of non-tribal high school students.
- 2) To find the level of achievement motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to background variables- gender, type of School, nature of School and fathers' occupation.
- 3) To find the significance difference in achievement motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to background variables- gender, type of School, nature of School and fathers' occupation.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) The level of Achievement motivation of non-tribal students is not high.
- 2) There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non-tribal school students with regard to gender.
- 3) There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non-tribal school students with regard to type of school.
- 4) There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non-tribal school students with regard to nature of school.
- 5) There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non-tribal school students with regard to fathers' occupational status

Population and Sample of the Study

The population for the present study is the students of standard IX in non-tribal areas of Namakkal District in Tamilnadu. From the population, the investigator has chosen 250 students using simple random sampling technique.

Tools Used for the Study

The researcher used Deo Mohan Achievement Motivation (n-Ach) scale. The original draft tool consisted of 115 items relating to Achievement Motivation with a 5 point scale. After the justification of validity, item analysis and item discrimination the final form of tool containing 50 items under 15 dimensions has been obtained. It was in English. It has been translated in to Tamil language also. The researcher has employed the test-retest method and the tool's reliability coefficient was discovered to be 0.73, and the scale's content validity was confirmed.

Data Collection Procedure

The investigator personally went to the schools. She received approval from the Headmaster and Headmistress. She then introduced herself to the children, explained the reason for her visit, the contents of the Bio-Data form, and the research tool with the aid of the teachers. Then she supplied the tools to the respondents and gathered data. Each school student was allowed to respond to all the items in the tool and Bio-Data form within one-hour duration.

Statistical Techniques Used

For the analysis of data following statistical techniques were adopted. They were,

- 1) Arithmetic mean
- 2) Percentage analysis
- 3) Standard Deviation and
- 4) ANOVA
- 5) 't'-test.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis – 1

The level of achievement motivation of non-tribal students is not high

Table 1: Level of Achievement motivation of non-tribal students

Variable	Low		Average		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Achievement Motivation	46	18.40	146	58.40	58	23.20

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From the above table – 1, it is found that majority of the students fall under the average category of achievement motivation.

Hypothesis – 2

There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non- tribal school students with regard to gender.

Table 2: Significance of Difference in Achievement Motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to gender.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Table value	Remark
Male	82	50.93	6.45	0.80	1.96	NS
Female	168	50.29	4.76			

From the above table -2, it is found that the calculated 't' value is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of non-tribal students with regard to gender.

Hypothesis – 3

There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non- tribal school students with regard to type of school.

Table 3: Significance of Difference in Achievement Motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to type of school

Type of school	Mean	df	Calculated 'F' value	Table value	Remark
Government	50.85	2,	1.95	3.04	NS
Aided	50.81	247			
Private	49.16				

From the above table -3, it is found that the calculated 'F' value is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of non-tribal students with regard to the type of school.

Hypothesis – 4

There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non- tribal school students with regard to Nature of schools.

Table 4: Significance of Difference in Achievement Motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to Nature of schools.

Nature of school	Mean	df	Calculated 'F' value	Table value	Remark
Boys	49.46	2,	1.39	3.04	NS
Girls	50.50	247			
Co-ed	51.01				

From the above table -4, it is found that the calculated 'F' value is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of non-tribal students with regard to the nature of school.

Hypothesis – 5

There is no significant difference in achievement motivation of non- tribal school students with regard to Father's Occupational status.

Table 5: Significance of Difference in Achievement Motivation of non-tribal high school students with regard to Father's Occupational status.

Father's Occupational Status	Mean	df	Calculated 'F' value	Table value	Remark
Low	51.06	2,	2.50	3.04	NS
Average	49.33	247			
High	50.03				

From the above table -5, it is found that the calculated 'F' value is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of non-tribal students with regard to Father's occupational status.

Findings of the Study

Considering the objectives and hypothesis, specific findings were enumerated from the results and interpretations of the present study as follows. From the percentage analysis majority of the students fall under the average category of achievement motivation. No significant difference found among the non-tribal students with regard to gender, type of schools, Nature of school and Fathers occupational status

Conclusion

On analysing the academic achievement, gender does not seem to have influenced the cognitive variable – academic achievement. But the other demographic variables - type of school, nature of school and father's occupation have significantly influenced the academic achievement of the students.

References

- [1] Dandapani, S. (2000). A Textbook of Advanced Educational Psychology. New Delhi: Anmol Publications Pvt Ltd.
- [2] Hurlock, E.B. (1978). Child Development (6 th ed.), New York: McGraw Hill Inc.,
- [3] Gupta, S.K. (1994). Applied Statistics for Educational Research. New Delhi: Mital Publications.
- [4] Alam, M. (2015). Research Aptitude. New Delhi: VEE Kumar Publications Pvt Ltd.
- [5] Best, J.W. & Jhan, J. V. (1995). Research in Education. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India.
- [6] International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research, 15(21), 495-507. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264839839_A_Study_of_Relationship_between_Achievement_Motivation_Self_Concept_and_Achievement_in_English_and_Mathematics_at_Secondary_Level
- [7] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303819754_Achievement_Motivation_of_College_Students_in_relation_to_their_Gender_Stream_and_Locale
- [8] Dissertation Abstracts International-A, Vol.67, No.10, April 2017, P.156

ROLE OF DIGITAL LEARNING IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

Digital learning" is a learning method based on the use of new digital tools to enable learners to learn in a different way, whether it be face-to-face, distance learning-asynchronous or synchronous. It is a type of learning that is accompanied by instructional practice that makes effective use of technology and it encompasses the application of a wide spectrum of practices, including blended and virtual learning. Digital education helps learners build the skills they need to navigate technology and to get the best out of it. Students of digital education become comfortable with finding, accessing, consuming and sharing content online. Digital Learning is learning facilitated by technology. Digital learning has revolutionized the Educational process by Reaching every child – wherever they live, however they learn. This paper tries to explore the role of Digital Learning in the present Educational system and the various learning possibilities of it. Moreover, this paper also tries to explain the various types of digital learning methods and how it enhances the individualized learning experience.

Keywords: *Digital Learning, Synchronous Learning, Asynchronous Learning*

Introduction

From the beginning of the COVID 19 pandemic ICT emerged as a path of deliverance for all the stakeholders in education- teachers, students, parents and the government all over the world. Devoid of direct interactions, academics shifted to online platforms like Google classroom and Zooms meetings. Today the educational systems around the world are under increasing pressure to use the ICTs to teach students the knowledge and the skills they need. UNESCO observes that “Digital technologies have evolved from stand-alone projects to networks of tools and programmes that connect people and things across the world, and help address personal and global challenges. Digital innovation has demonstrated powers to complement, enrich and transform education, and has the potential to speed up progress towards Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) for education and transform modes of provision of universal access to learning. It can enhance the quality and relevance of learning, strengthen inclusion, and improve education administration and governance. In times of crises, distance learning can mitigate the effects of education disruption and school closures.”

Digital Learning

The incorporation of technology in the classroom is a process that involves changes in the education system and occurs over a period of time. Technology provides new characteristics that can be applied by a teacher to make it more attractive to students. One of them is by using digital learning. Digital learning is a learning technology; students learn digitally both online and offline, anytime and anywhere. Digital learning can include theory eBooks, videos, online assessments, online simulations, certificates, and others. The digital transformation has completely opened up the field of learning possibilities. Our relationship with education and training has changed profoundly and new technologies now allow us to learn anywhere. Digital learning is the digitalization of the entire learning experience: social learning, virtual meetings with professionals, online exams, networking with alumni, professionalization workshops, etc. To be successful in the workplace of the future, people will need to have the right digital education. Whether in school, at university or on the job – the digital transformation that is under way is making IT skills more important every day. Digital media are also creating new opportunities for digital learning. Digital learning tools can be effectively used for ‘In class learning’, ‘Out of the class learning’ and ‘In deep learning’ situations. ICT used in Digital learning process has revolutionized the learning spaces with the introduction of Learning Management Systems (LMS) and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs).

Importance of Digital Learning

Digital tools and platforms are becoming ever more integral to our personal and working lives. Digital learning increases access to education and knowledge while empowering students with a mindset and capabilities that sets them up for success in their present and future. Plenty of data suggests that simply giving learners access to devices doesn't necessarily lead to better outcomes; thoughtful integration and actively adopting a digital mindset is needed for digital learning to truly enhance the overall student experience. The

digital education system makes the assessment of each and every student much more transparent and informative with real-time performance. . It offers the students the capability to measure their performance in detail and come up with relevant solutions on their part . As well as being able to access learning anytime, from anywhere, digital education also enables students to learn at their own pace. They can re-read materials to gain a deeper grounding in a topic or even revisit earlier modules. E-learning makes use of different platforms , which provides interactive content. Also, you can share your thoughts and opinions with others. The more engaging the lessons, the more students can remember the information.

Characteristics of Digital Learning

Digital learning encompasses a wide spectrum of tools and practices, digital learning emphasizes high quality instruction and provides access to challenge content, feedback through formative assessment, opportunities for anytime and anywhere.

- 1) Personal and flexible
- 2) Led by teachers with significant support
- 3) Flexible and high quality resources
- 4) Collaboration and sharing
- 5) Confined to web based and internet based learning

Types

E-Textbook – EtextbookS is an updated and modern version of traditional textbooks. Numerous research studies by colleges and other educational institutions found that e-textbooks will soon surpass traditional textbooks. e-textbooks are better because they are cost-effective, easy to use and handle, non-perishable, and very easy to update to keep pace with changing scenarios.

Mobile Learning

As the name suggests, this involves training from your smartphone. A practice particularly suited to the "anytime, anywhere, anyplace" learning experience.

Online Classroom

Online classrooms are created through learning management systems and allow your learners and trainers to connect online. This could be done through either synchronous interactions or asynchronous messages. This is a great digital learning option to consider when you have a global workforce that works remotely.

Virtual Classroom

Based on the principle of traditional synchronous training, virtual classes allow trainers and learners to be brought together in the same virtual place, for example during a video conference.

Conclusion

We must change not only what we learn, but also how we learn. Whether this involves digital platforms, virtual or augmented reality, online libraries or webinars – digital media make possible a host of new and innovative forms of teaching and learning in schools, vocational institutions and universities as well as in corporate training and development programs. Digital learning means more than just digitizing traditional instruction materials. Using digital media in education will result in completely new areas of communication, cooperation and networking. Since digital instruction is not bound by time and place, it is more flexible, more individualized and more mobile than traditional forms of learning. Rennie and Keith clearly states “In the larger educational milieu, digital opportunities for learning are multiplying in Primary and Secondary schools, in the workplace and in non-formal, self-directed learning. Undoubtedly, our thinking will change many times in the next few years as our understanding of this global digital educational environment evolves, but neither educators nor learners can afford to ignore or look on from the edges.”

References

- [1] Frank Rennie & Keith Smyth, Digital Learning: The Key Concepts (2nd Edition): London: Routledge 2020
- [2] Edutrack, a monthly scanner of trends in education, June 2022, Vol.21.No.10
- [3] Edutrack , a monthly scanner of trends in education, October 2022, Vol 22 No.2
- [4] European Journal of Special Needs Education, Volume 36,2021 Issue 1
- [5] Michael Thomas &Mark Warschauer: Digital Education and Learning, 2020

IMPROVING INTEGRATED SCIENCE PROCESSES THROUGH INFOTAINMENT STRATEGIES AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to enhance the integrated science process skills through infotainment approaches for the undergraduate student. It is a experimental research design conducted on the 42 undergraduate second year students who are studying B.Sc. physics in alagappa arts college, karaikudi. It made use of purposive random sampling in selecting 42 students. The six prominent integrated science process skills used in the study are: Controlling variables, Defining operationally, Formulating hypotheses, Interpreting data, experimenting and Formulating models are the integrated science process skills used in this present study. An infotainment content were developed to enhance the integrated science process skills. The post test were conducted after the intervention. Data analysis involved the use of mean, SD, ' t ' test and effect size are calculated by cohen's *d* to investigate the difference between the means. From the statistical findings the result indicate the integrated science process skills are highly enhanced with the infotainment strategies among the undergraduate students and it significantly enhanced the students learning achievement and desirable affective outcomes. Furthermore, it was found that the proposed approach did not increase students' cognitive load.

Keywords: *Integrated Science Process, Infotainment Strategies And Undergraduate Students.*

Introduction

The term *infotainment* refers to a cluster of program types that blur traditional distinctions between information-oriented and entertainment-based genres of television programming. Infotainment is often used to denote the decline of hard news and public affairs discussion programs and the corresponding development of a variety of entertainment shows that mimic the style of news. At the same time, however, the early years of the twenty-first century have seen the increasing emergence of programs that more thoroughly blend the content and form of various genres of public affairs and entertainment. Similarly in the education field will be get better pedagogical experience by the implication of infotainment approach. Science process occurs naturally, spontaneously in our minds. By logically breaking down the steps in our thinking, we can use science process to find out how to answer our questions about how the world works. Science process is not just useful in science, but in any situation that requires critical thinking.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the effect of infotainment strategies in enhancing integrated science process skills among under graduate students.
- 2) To find out there is any significant difference between the mean scores of each test in before and after intervention.
- 3) To find out the effect size of each test of each integrated science process skills.

Hypothesis of the Study

- 1) There is significant difference among the controlling variable skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.
- 2) There is significant difference among the Defining operationally skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.
- 3) There is significant difference among the Formulating hypotheses skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.
- 4) There is significant difference among the Interpreting data skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.
- 5) There is significant difference among the experimenting skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.
- 6) There is significant difference among the Formulating models skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Methodology

The study is restricted to the enhancing integrated science process skills through infotainment strategies only on undergraduate students. The process skill of science infotainment intervention are focused on during the 20 working days of the experiment has done as contained in the current syllabus followed by alagappa university karaikudi. This study employed a single group experimental research design. The specific design the researcher employed is a pre-test, progressive test and post-test.

Sample

The sampling technique adopted of this study is simple random sampling technique. The total sample of 42 students from studying IInd B.Sc, physics in alagappa arts college karaikudi.

Tool Used for the Present Study

- 1) A questionnaire of “Developed science process skill test”
- 2) Infotainment strategies developed by ICEBERG INFOTAINMENT Ltd, Bijus application LMES Academy and Amasci were used as tools for the present study.

Statistical Techniques

The mean, SD, ‘ t ’ test and effect size are calculated by cohen’s *d* to investigate the difference between the means these are the statistical techniques were used to arrive the empirical findings of this present study.

Cohen’s *d* Effect Size Calculation

For the independent samples T-test, Cohen's *d* is determined by calculating the mean difference between your two groups, and then dividing the result by the *pooled* standard deviation.

$$\text{Cohen's } d = (M_2 - M_1) / SD_{\text{pooled}}$$

where:

$$SD_{\text{pooled}} = \sqrt{((SD_1^2 + SD_2^2) / 2)}$$

Cohen's *d* is the appropriate effect size measure if two groups have similar standard deviations and are of the same size.

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis 1: There is significant difference among the controlling variable skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.1 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students of controlling variable skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of significance
1	Controlling Variable	42	Pre-Test	40.36	3.78	5.09	21.30	Significant
			Progressive Test	62.87	4.98			
2			Progressive Test	62.87	4.98	3.82	16.00	Significant
			Post Test	82.33	5.19			
3			Pre-Test	40.36	3.78	9.24	38.67	Significant
			Post Test	82.33	5.19			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated ‘t’ values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at

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0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the controlling variable skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is significant difference among the Defining operationally skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.2 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students of Defining operationally skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of significance
1	Defining operationally	42	Pre-Test	45.98	4.22	3.54	14.83	Significant
			Progressive Test	62.35	4.98			
2			Progressive Test	62.35	4.98	3.34	13.98	Significant
			Post Test	80.21	5.68			
3			Pre-Test	45.98	4.22	6.84	28.61	Significant
			Post Test	80.21	5.68			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated 't' values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the Defining operationally skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is significant difference among the Formulating hypotheses skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.3 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students of Formulating hypotheses skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of Significance
1	Formulating hypotheses	42	Pre-Test	41.02	4.26	3.28	13.74	Significant
			Progressive Test	56.25	4.98			
2			Progressive Test	56.25	4.98	3.03	12.67	Significant
			Post Test	72.36	5.63			
3			Pre-Test	41.02	4.26	6.27	23.28	Significant
			Post Test	72.36	5.63			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated 't' values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the Formulating

hypotheses skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is significant difference among the Interpreting data skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.4 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students Interpreting data skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of Significance
1	Interpreting data	42	Pre-Test	32.66	3.65	3.07	12.87	Significant
			Progressive Test	45.65	4.72			
2			Progressive Test	45.65	4.72	4.56	19.10	
			Post Test	69.52	5.69			
3			Pre-Test	32.66	3.65	7.71	32.25	
			Post Test	69.52	5.69			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated 't' values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the Interpreting data skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Hypothesis 5: There is significant difference among the experimenting skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.5 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students of experimenting skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of Significance
1	Experimenting	42	Pre-Test	48.58	3.21	3.16	13.23	Significant
			Progressive Test	61.22	4.65			
2			Progressive Test	61.22	4.65	3.13	13.12	
			Post Test	78.25	6.11			
3			Pre-Test	48.58	3.21	6.07	25.43	
			Post Test	78.25	6.11			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated 't' values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the experimenting skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated

science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Hypothesis 6: There is significant difference among the Formulating models skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

Table 1.6 shows the mean, SD, effect size and t-value of the total sample students of Formulating models skill of the total sample in the pre vs progressive, progressive vs post and pre vs post tests.

S. No	Skill	N	Test	Mean	SD	Effect Size	T value	Level of Significance
1	Formulating models	42	Pre-Test	46.09	4.77	2.57	10.75	Significant
			Progressive Test	59.33	5.50			
2			Progressive Test	59.33	5.50	3.10	12.97	Significant
			Post Test	78.65	6.88			
3			Pre-Test	46.09	4.77	5.50	23.00	Significant
			Post Test	78.65	6.88			

Significant and Not Significant level at 0.05=1.697

Interpretation

From the above table, it is understood that the effect size of pre-test vs posttest is found to be high. Similarly all the calculated 't' values with the degrees of freedom 40 are higher than the table value 1.697 at 0.05 significant level. Hence, it is inferred that there exist significant difference between the Formulating models skill and it is concluded that the infotainment strategy having more effectiveness in enhancing the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. Hence, the hypothesis framed by the investigator is accepted.

Conclusion

Finally this study concluded that the infotainment strategies are highly enhanced the integrated science process skills among the undergraduate students. In the findings the six prominent integrated process skills are developed to the samples of the students. In the all tables of this study examined that there is more differences in the pre-test and the post-test such it is conclude that infotainment strategies are much effective in enhancing the integrated process skills.

Reference

- [1] Al-rabaani, A. (2014). The acquisition of science process skills by Omani's pre-service social studies' teachers. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(1), 13-19.
- [2] Feyzioglu, B., Demirdag, B., Akyildiz, M., & Altun, E. (2012). Developing a of a science process skills test for secondary students: validity and reliability study. *Educational sciences: Theory and Practice*, 12(3), 1899-1906.
- [3] Monica, K. (2005). Development and validation of a test of integrated science process skills for the further education and training learners. Unpublished Master's thesis, University of Pretoria. South Africa.
- [4] Ozgelen, S. (2012). Students science process skills within a cognitive domain framework. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science& Technology Education*, 8(4), 283-292. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2012.846a>
- [5] Sathyaraj.K. and Dr.R.Ramnath. (2016). "infotainment strategies in enhancing science process skills among the undergraduate students", *Research in Science and Technological Education*, 19, 133-145.
- [6] Sathyaraj.K. and Dr.R.Ramnath. (2017). "Promoting Process Skills Of Physics Through Infotainment Strategies Among Higher Secondary Students", *EDU APEX [J]*, 19, 133-145.
- [7] Sathyaraj.K. and Dr.R.Ramnath. (2017). "promoting creativity in learning through infotainment strategies", *enhancement of creativity in learning:Applications of innovative pedagogy*, 46-49.

REASONING ABILITY AMONG THE STATE UNIVERSITIES RESEARCH SCHOLARS IN MATHEMATICS

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Abstract

The present education system focuses the online related teaching-learning methods. Reasoning is the ability to utilize the past experiences in the drawing of practical and theoretical conclusion and to solve problems and also the ability of acting effectively given condition. The study's main objective is to determine the reasoning ability and performance in mathematics among the state universities of Tamilnadu research scholars. A sample of 300 research scholars from 22 state universities in Tamilnadu state is selected randomly for the study. Data were analysed using percentage analysis and t-test. Findings reveal that the significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars in terms of its dimensions of verbal thinking, numerical thinking, analytical thinking, critical thinking, analogy thinking but there is no significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars regarding total. Reasoning ability are a sustainable development in the future, even in a virus outbreak, storm, torrent, world war, etc.

Keywords: Reasoning Ability, State University, Research Scholars, Mathematics

Introduction

According to Win Sent "Reasoning is the ability to utilize the past experiences in the drawing of practical and theoretical conclusion and to solve problems and also the ability of acting effectively given condition (Buckingham). Spearman's g-factor in his General Factor Theory or the Theory of two factors (Spearman, 1904) is connected with reasoning ability: Since most tests that proved loadings on g implied abstract reasoning, he concluded that g was an essential part of human intelligence. Spearman documented empirical support for his thesis (Spearman, 1927) by presenting a correlation of .84 of Otis (1918) between tests containing analogies and g. Raven (1936) constructed his first figural matrices test, the Standard Progressive Matrices, according to Spearman's theory, designing the tasks in order to capture the factors of intelligence defined by Spearman. Thurstone (1938), in his Primary Factor Model, interpreted one of his seven primary abilities as reasoning and detecting rules. He defined induction as rule finding. In Thurstone's model, according to Wilhelm (2005), "the reasoning factor is marked mostly by inductive tasks" (p. 377). In the Three-Stratum Theory of Carroll (1993), fluid intelligence is - to a certain degree - defined by reasoning ability that in turn consists of three factors from the lowest stratum: sequential reasoning, induction, and quantitative reasoning. This structure can also be found in the model of Horn and Cattell (1966) apart from that their model does not provide a level of higher generality and thus no g. Reasoning ability (G f) is the fundamental component for the more specific factors that can be measured by several tasks. Ridley and et.al (1992). Reasoning Ability skills mean the skills attained by the students in analysing, reasoning and evaluating the effectiveness of learning strategies whenever and wherever necessary.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the significant difference, if any, in the reasoning ability concerning gender
- 2) To find out the significant difference, if any, in performance in mathematics concerning gender.
- 3) To find out the significant relationship between reasoning ability and performance in mathematics of state universities research scholars.

Null Hypotheses

- 1) There is no significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars in terms of its dimensions.
- 2) There is no significant difference between male and female state universities research scholars concerning mathematics performance.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between reasoning ability and performance in mathematics of state universities research scholars.

Review of Related Literature

Wulandari (2018) the students have good reasoning skills to analyse, to generalize, to synthesize, to justify, and to solve a non-routine problem (62.69%, 66.67%, 48.15%, 24.07%, and 3.70 respectively). There are some factors influence the different level of students reasoning skills including their ability to identify information in the question, use mathematical arguments to explain the answer and identify the strategy to solve problems. Kanimozhi, Ganesan (2017) This study focused on “The present study is a survey in nature to find out reasoning ability among higher secondary students in Madurai District. The tool is of a multiple-choice type consisting of 50 items. The investigator selected a stratified random sample of 303 higher secondary students for the study. The findings revealed that among higher secondary students 61.38 % of them are poor in reasoning ability, 21.45 % of them are average in reasoning ability, 16.5% of students are very poor in reasoning ability and only 0.66 % of students are good in reasoning ability. There exists a positive correlation between mathematical achievement and reasoning ability.

Methodology

The target group was a research scholar in the state universities of Tamil Nadu in India. State Universities of Tamil Nadu research scholars selected with the random sampling technics. University grant commission was considered as some universities are under the state universities of Tamil Nadu (Mookkiah, M., & Prabu, M. M. 2020). At present, 22 universities are under the state universities of Tamil Nadu. In the state universities of Tamil Nadu, almost 98,00 research scholars in the recent academic year. As used random sampling technics and choose 200 research scholars in education were randomly selected from the state universities of Tamil Nadu in India. Concurrently, the survey conducts through the website, so any student interested could also meet the same questionnaires (Hybrid mode) offline and online version. hence, the number of completions included both printed hard copy and soft copy surveys. The investigator develops the tool for using reasoning ability and performance in mathematics scales.

Results and Discussion

Difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars in terms of its dimensions

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Table value	Remarks
Verbal Thinking	Male	104	28.00	1.980	18.91	1.972	Significant
	Female	96	23.00	1.780			
Numerical Thinking	Male	104	20.00	2.980	2.868	1.972	Significant
	Female	96	19.00	1.778			
Analytical Thinking	Male	104	18.00	1.857	12.356	1.972	Significant
	Female	96	21.00	1.584			
Critical Thinking	Male	104	16.00	0.857	11.422	1.972	Significant
	Female	96	14.00	1.584			
Analogy Thinking	Male	104	19.520	2.857	13.245	1.972	Significant
	Female	96	14.950	1.925			
Total	Male	104	20.304	2.106	0.665	1.972	Not significant
	Female	96	18.39	1.730			

(Table value at 5% level of significance is 1.972)

At 5% level of significance, the table value of ‘t’ is 1.97. It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars in terms of its dimensions of verbal thinking, numerical thinking, analytical thinking, critical thinking, analogy thinking. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. But there is no significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars regarding total. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Difference between male and female state universities research scholars concerning mathematics performance

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Table value	Remarks
Male	104	55.2500	23.239	0.992	1.972	Not significant
Female	96	51.8854	24.741			

At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.97. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female state universities research scholars concerning mathematics performance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Difference between reasoning ability and performance in mathematics of state universities research scholars

Variables	'r' value	Table value	N	Remark
Reasoning ability vs Performance in Mathematics	0.728	0.113	200	Significant

At 5% level of significance, the table value of 'r' is 0.113. It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant relationship between reasoning ability and performance in mathematics of state universities research scholars. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

Today research scholars are reorganized as one of the most important aspects of the society as they are linked with huge task of educating the younger generation (Mani, M. and Prabu, M.M., 2019). The college administrator plays a key role in the development and improvement of the scholars. He monitors variety of people including Professors, research scholars, management and parents, where he should possess the positive relationship. In the present study, the researcher has made an attempt to investigate the reasoning ability of state universities research scholars. The t test reveals that there is a significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars in terms of its dimensions of verbal thinking, numerical thinking, analytical thinking, critical thinking, analogy thinking but there is no significant difference between reasoning ability male and female state universities research scholars regarding total. There is no significant difference between male and female state universities research scholars concerning mathematics performance. There is no significant relationship between reasoning ability and performance in mathematics of state universities research scholars.

References

- [1] Wulandari, F. E., & Shofiyah, N. (2018, April). Problem-based learning: effects on student's scientific reasoning skills in science. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1006, No. 1, p. 012029). IOP Publishing.
- [2] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2019). Teachers self-efficacy scale: development and validation. *Review of Research*, 8(6), 1-8.
- [3] Spearman, F. H. (1904). *The Strategy of Great Railroads*. C. Scribner's sons.
- [4] Mookkiah, M., & Kumar, S. (2021). YOGA BASED INTERVENTION STRATEGIES IN ACCELERATING SELF-EFFICACY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(4).
- [5] Kanimozhi, P., & Ganesan, P. (2017). Reasoning ability among higher secondary students. *International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah*, 5(6), 471-475.
- [6] Mookkiah, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2020). Impact of Social Media on the Academic Achievement of secondary school students. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, 12(3), 3106-3109.
- [7] Bhat, M. A. (2016). The predictive power of reasoning ability on academic achievement. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 15(1).
- [8] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2019). A Study On Self Efficacy Of Higher Secondary Students With Respect To Locality Of The Schools. *Think India Journal*, 22(10), 807-813.

EFFECT OF CIRCUIT TRAINING ON MUSCULAR STRENGTH AMONG COLLEGE LEVEL ATHLETES

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effect of circuit training on muscular strength among college level athletes. To achieve the purpose of the study thirty college level male athletes were selected from Government Degree College, karvetinagaram, Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh, India during the year 2022. The students, who has taken as a subjects age ranged from 18 to 25 years. The selected athletes were divided into two equal groups consists of 15 subjects each namely experimental group and control group. The experimental group underwent Circuit training for twelve weeks. The control group was not taking any training. In this study Muscular strength was taken as criterion variable. The selected athletes were tested on muscular strength was measured through modified sit ups test. Pre-test score was taken before the training period and post- test score was measured immediately after the twelve weeks training period. Statistical technique 't' ratio was used to analyse the means of the pre-test data and post test data of experimental group and control group. The results were showed that there was a significant difference found on the criterion variable. The difference is found due to Circuit training given to the experimental group on muscular strength when compared to control group.

Keywords: *Circuit Training, Muscular Strength And 'T' Ratio.*

Introduction

Strength and conditioning programs have evolved from mainly strength training into well attention exposed, periodized programmes that central on using a variety of modalities to improve athletic performance. While there a vast number of modalities that may be utilize in a sport performance program, the most common seem to be strength training, Olympic weightlifting, plyometrics, and agility exercises. The periodization scheme used may follow linear or undulating values. Common equipment used in strength and conditioning program differ broadly depending on space, setting, and financial resources. Equipment might include squat racks, barbells, dumbbells, boxes, and objects of different weights. However the goal of these methods and equipment is to enhance sports performance.

Research Methodology

Selection of Subjects

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Circuit training on muscular strength among college level students. To achieve this purpose of the study. College level students were selected as subjects at random. The athletes, who has taken as a subjects age ranged from 18 to 25 years.

Selection of variable	
Independent variable	Circuit Training
Dependent variable	Muscular Strength

Experimental Design and Implementation

The selected subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen subjects each, such as a Resisted Sprint training group (Experimental Group) and control group. The experimental group underwent resisted sprint training for three days per week for Twelve weeks. The control group was not taking any training. The following physical variable namely muscular strength was selected as criterion variable. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected criterion variable Muscular strength was measured through modified sit ups test at prior to and immediately after the training programme.

Statistical Technique

The't' test has used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively.

Level of Significance

The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was measured as an appropriate.

Analysis of the Data

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group has found out by pre-test. The data had analysed and dependent 't' test has used with 0.05 levels as

Confidence

The basis of this results obtained the following conclusions are drawn,

- 1) There was a significant difference between experimental and control group on Muscular strength after the training period.
- 2) There was a significant improvement on muscular strength. However the Improvement was in favour of experimental group due to eight weeks of resisted sprint training.

Table I Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post test scores of experimental and control group on Muscular strength (Scores in numbers)

Variable	Group	Mean		Standard Deviation		df	't' ratio	P value
		pre	post	pre	post			
		Muscular Strength	Control	37.53	38.26			
	Experimental	38.73	41.60	1.70	1.45	14	8.911	0.001**

*Significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

The mean of pre test and post test experimental group were 38.73 and 41.60 respectively. The pre test and post test means for control group were 37.53 and 38.26 as shown in the table – I. The mean difference between experimental and control group are 2.867 and 0.73 and p- value is lower than 0.05 in Experimental Group. This means that there was statistically significant rise in athlete scores in the post test in experimental group. In control group p-value is greater than 0.05. This means that there was statistically no significant in athlete post test scores. The obtained 't' ratio was 8.911* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.145 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant.

Discussions on Findings

The result of the study shows that the experimental group, namely Circuit training group had significantly improved the selected dependent variable that is muscular strength, when compared to the control group. It is also found that the improvement caused by resisted sprint training when compared to the control group.

Conclusion

The basis of the results obtained the following conclusions are drawn,

- 1) There was a significant difference between experimental and control group on muscular strength after the training period.
- 2) The p-value is less than the significant value 0.05 in Experimental group and p-value is greater than the significant value 0.05 in control group.
- 3) There was a significant improvement on muscular strength. However the improvement was in favour of experimental group due to twelve weeks of circuit training.

References

- [1] Vishal Kumar (2016) Impact of yogic practices and circuit training on power production and health care. International Journal Physical Education Sports Health;3(1):302-304.
- [2] Binodh and Danaraj.(2016). Influence of bulgarian bag training on selected strength parameters and performance variables among volleyball players.International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Review, 1(19), pp. 22-24.

EFFECT OF ASSISTED AND RESISTED SPRINT TRAINING ON ACCELERATION ABILITY AMONG INTERCOLLEGIATE ATHLETES

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of assisted and resisted sprint training on Acceleration ability performance among college athlete in Andhra Pradesh. For the purpose of the study sixty(N=60) athletes studying various affiliated colleges to Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh state, India, were randomly selected as subjects. The subjects were assigned into four groups of fifteen each. Group-I assigned Assisted Sprint Training, Group-II assigned Resisted Sprint Training, Group-III assigned combined Assisted and Resisted Sprint Training and Group-IV acted as Control. Acceleration ability only selected as a dependent variable and it was assessed by 30 meters sprint test. The Experimental groups undergo their respective training for twelve weeks duration. And the number of session was conformed into 3 days per week. At moment when all the subjects were tested previous to and immediately than the training for the selected variable. Data were collected and statistically analyzed by ANCOVA. Scheffe's post hoc test was applied to find out the significant difference between the paired means, in all the cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference among all the Experimental groups' namely assisted sprint training, resisted sprint training and combined (AST & RST). The results showed group Assisted sprint training group was found to have greater impact on the group concerned than the Resisted sprint training group, combined assisted and resisted training and control group in enhancing the performance of Acceleration ability.

Keywords: *Assisted, Resisted, Combined Training, Acceleration Ability.*

Introduction

Resisted sprint (RS) preparing is usually utilized as a way to increasing speed in running. This strategy for preparing may include the competitor run with an additional heap utilizing a weighted sledge, a weighted vest, or a speed parachute, or performing tough or sand rise preparing. The basic presumption in Resisted sprint training preparing is that it will in the end lead to increments in walk length amid typical opposed running, by expanding the power and quality. In spite of the fact that Resisted sprint training preparing is regularly drilled over a wide assortment of games, review of the writing indicates constrained logical proof to help the utilization of RS preparing as a strategy for speed advancement. Different examinations have concentrated on the impact of RS preparing on the kinematics of dashing, however there is little research looking at the more extended term impacts of RS preparing program on quality and running rate execution (Costello, 1985). On the track and in team sports, resisted sprinting is a common means of providing a sprint-specific overload stimulus. While there are several methods of applying resistance, the most common are sleds. Unfortunately, in both research and practice the way loads are regularly prescribed is still years behind the gym-based approach (Cahill, 2019).

Methodology

For the purpose of the study sixty(N=60) athletes studying various affiliated colleges to Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh state, India, were randomly selected as subjects. The subjects were divided into four groups. Group-I underwent AST (n=15), Group-II underwent RST (n=15), Group-III underwent combined Assisted and Resisted Sprint Training (n=15) and Group-IV acted as Control. Speed only selected as a dependent variable and it was assessed through 30 meters sprint test. The experimental groups underwent their respective training for 12 weeks period and Three days per week. All the subjects were tested before and after than the training for the selected variable.

Analysis of the Data

The data collected from the experimental groups and control group on prior and after experimentation on selected variables were statistically examined by analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to determine differences, if any among the adjusted post test means on selected criterion variables separately. Whenever they obtained f-ratio value was significant the Scheffe's test was applied as post hoc test to determine the paired mean differences, if any. In all the cases 0.05 level of significance was fixed. The results of the Analysis of Covariance on Acceleration ability of the pre, post, and adjusted test scores of Assisted Sprint

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Training group, Resisted Sprint Training group and Combined Assisted and Resisted Sprint Training group and Control group are presented in Table –1.

Acceleration Ability

The data collected during the pre and post test period among assisted, resisted and combined assisted and resisted sprint training groups and control group on acceleration ability have been statistically analyzed and the details are presented in Table–I.

Table – I Analysis of Covariance on Acceleration Ability of Assisted Resisted and Combined Sprint Training Groups and Control Group

		AST	RST	Combined	Control	SOV	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	F ratio
Pre test	Mean	4.80	4.90	4.89	4.91	B	0.004	3	0.001	0.25
	SD	0.09	0.09	0.05	0.04	W	0.19	36	0.006	
Post test	Mean	4.55	4.70	4.68	4.86	B	0.54	3	0.18	32.90
	SD	0.11	0.04	0.05	0.06	W	0.20	36	0.006	
Adjusted Post test	Mean	4.50	4.71	4.61	4.87	B	0.53	3	0.18	35.04
						W	0.17	35	0.0050	

*Significant at .05 level of confidence

(The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degree of freedom 3 and 36 is 2.87 and degrees of freedom 3 and 35 is 2.87)

Table–I shows that the pre test means and standard deviation on acceleration ability of assisted sprint training group, resisted sprint training group, combined assisted and resisted sprint training group and control group are 4.90 ± 0.09 , 4.80 ± 0.09 , 4.91 ± 0.05 and 4.89 ± 0.04 in that order. The attained ‘F’ ratio assessment of 0.25 was not as much of the essential table score of 2.87 for the quantity of freedom 3 and 36 at 0.05 level of assurance, which shows that the casual mission of the subjects were a success because the pre check scores on acceleration ability among groups didn’t vary drastically. The post test means and standard deviation on acceleration ability of assisted sprint training group, resisted sprint training group, combined assisted and resisted sprint training group and control group are 4.54 ± 0.11 , 4.71 ± 0.04 , 4.68 ± 0.05 and 4.87 ± 0.06 respectively. The attained ‘F’ ratio assessment of 32.90 on acceleration ability was as much of the essential table score of 2.87 for the quantity of freedom 3 and 36 at 0.05 level of assurance. It implies that momentous variation existed between the groups during the post test phase on acceleration ability. The adjusted post-test means on acceleration ability of assisted sprint training, resisted sprint training, combined assisted and resisted sprint training and control groups are 4.50, 4.71, 4.61 and 4.87 respectively. The attained ‘F’ ratio assessment is 35.04 of acceleration ability was as much of the essential table score of 2.87 for the quantity of freedom 3 and 35 at 0.05 level of assurance. The outcome of the study tells that, major differences be present among experimental and control groups on acceleration ability.

Table – II Scheffé S Test for the Differences between the Adjusted Post Test Paired Means on Acceleration Ability

Adjusted Post Test Mean				Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
Assisted Sprint Training	Resisted Sprint Training	Combined Sprint Training	Control Group		
4.50	4.71			0.21*	0.09
4.50		4.61		0.11*	0.09
4.50			4.87	0.37*	0.09
	4.71	4.61		0.10*	0.09
	4.71		4.87	0.16*	0.09
		4.61	4.87	0.16*	0.09

*Significant at .05 level.

Table–II shows that the adjusted post test mean differences on acceleration ability between assisted

and resisted sprint training groups, assisted and combined sprint training groups, assisted sprint training and control groups; resisted and combined sprint training groups, resisted sprint training and control groups; combined sprint training and control groups are 0.21, 0.11, 0.37, 0.10, 0.16 and 0.16 respectively, which are greater than the confidence interval value of 0.09.

Conclusion

From the result of the study it was concluded that the acceleration ability of the assisted, resisted and combined sprint training group subjects was significantly changed when compared with the control group. However, when comparing the experimental groups there was significant differences existed among them in improving the acceleration ability. Among the experimental group assisted sprint training had high impact to increase the acceleration ability of the subjects.

References

- [1] Whitney Leyva, D., Megan Wong, A., and Lee E Brown., (2017). Resisted and Assisted Training for Sprint Speed. *Journal of Physical Fitness, Medicine & Treatment in Sports*. 1 (1): 1-6.
- [2] Upton, D.E., (2011). The effect of assisted and resisted sprint training on acceleration and velocity in Division IA female soccer athletes. *J Strength Cond Res*. 25 (10): 2645-2652.
- [3] Spinks et.al (2007), "The effects of resisted sprint training on acceleration performance and kinematics in soccer, rugby union, and Australian football players." *J. Strength Cond. Res*. 21(1):77-85.
- [4] Ramkrishna, N., and Bujurke, A.G., (2019). Effect of assisted and resisted sprint training on anaerobic power performance of athletes. *International Journal of Yogic, Human Movement and Sports Sciences*. 4(1): 264-266.

EFFECT OF STEP AEROBIC TRAINING ON SELECTED PHYSICAL VARIABLE AMONG MIDDLE DISTANCE RUNNERS

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Abstract

For this purpose of the study thirty subjects were selected from Karaikkudi District. The subject's age group between 18 to 23 years. All the subjects were tested on selected physical and physiological variables. The selected 30 subjects were divided into two groups, namely experimental group and control group. Each group consists of 15 players and each the subjects were pre tested for their Physical and Variables. An intentional programmer of Step Aerobic Training experimental Group and the control Group was not given any experimental treatment. After the experimental period of Six Weeks, post-tests scores were obtained from all the two groups. The difference between initial and final scores on Step Aerobic training on selected Physical and Variables among Middle Distance Runners.

Introduction

A sport is an organized, competitive, entertaining and skillful physical activity requiring commitment, strategy and fair play in which a winner can be defined by objective means. It is governed by a set of rules or customs. In sports the key factors are the physical capabilities and skills of the competitor when determining the outcome (winning or losing). The physical activity involves the movement of people, animals and/or a variety of objects such as balls and machines or equipment. In contrast, games such as card games and board games, though these could be called mind sports and some are recognized as Olympic sports, require primarily mental skills and only mental physical involvement. Non-competitive activities, for example as jogging or playing catch are usually classified as forms of recreation. Physical events such as scoring goals or crossing a line first often define the result of a sport. However, the degree of skill and performance in some sports such as diving, dressage and figure skating is judged according to well-defined criteria. This is in contrast with other judged activities such as beauty pageants and body building, where skill does not have to be shown and the criteria are not as well defined. Records are kept and updated for most sports at the highest levels, while failures and accomplishments are widely announced in sport news.

Bahenský, P (2020) we evaluated the effect of an eleven-day altitude training camp on aerobic and anaerobic fitness in trained adolescent runners. Twenty adolescent (14–18 yrs) middle- and long-distance runners (11 males and 9 females; 16.7 ± 0.8 yrs), with at least two years of self-reported consistent run training, participated in this study. Eight of the subjects (4 females/4 males) constituted the control group, whereas twelve subjects (5 females/7 males) took part in a structured eleven-day altitude training camp, and training load was matched between groups. Primary variables of interest included changes in aerobic (VO_{2max}) and anaerobic (30 s Wingate test) power. We also explored the relationships between running velocity and blood lactate levels before and after the altitude training camp. Following 11 days of altitude training, desirable changes ($p < 0.01$) in VO_{2max} (+13.6%), peak relative work rate (+9.6%), and running velocity at various blood lactate concentrations (+5.9%–9.6%) were observed. Meanwhile, changes in Wingate anaerobic power (+5.1%) were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Short duration altitude appears to yield meaningful improvements in aerobic but not anaerobic power in trained adolescent endurance runners

Selection of Subjects

For this purpose of the study thirty subjects were selected from Karaikkudi District. The subject's age group between 18 to 23 years. All the subjects were tested on selected physical and physiological variables.

Experimental Design

The selected 30 subjects were divided into two groups, namely experimental group and control group. Each group consists of 15 players and each the subjects were pre tested for their Physical and Variables. An intentional programmer of Step Aerobic Training experimental Group and the control Group was not given any experimental treatment. After the experimental period of Six Weeks, post-tests scores were obtained from all the two groups. The difference between initial and final scores on Step Aerobic training on selected Physical and Variables among Middle Distance Runners.

Analysis of 't'-ratio the Pre and Post-Test for Control and Experimental group on Speed Endurance

Variables	Groups	Mean		Sd		Sd Error	df	T Ratio
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post			
Speed Endurance	Control	46.46	46.45	1.39	1.24	0.06	14	0.24
	Experimental	46.62	45.57	0.86	0.81	0.09		10.99*

*Significance at 0.05 level of confidence

The Table 4.1 shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of control group on speed endurance was 46.46 and 46.45 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 0.24, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.15 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre-test and post-test of experimental groups on speed endurance was 46.62 and 45.57 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 10.99* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.15 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between control group and experimental group in speed endurance. It may be concluded from the result of the study that experimental group improved in speed endurance due to six weeks of Step Aerobic Training.

Bar Diagram Shows the Pre and Post Test Mean values of Control group and Experimental on Speed Endurance

References

- [1] Bisht, S., & Sharma, M. A. 2020. A Study of Effect of Uphill Running Training and Staircase Training on Vital Capacity. *Int. J. Phy. Edu. Spo*, 4(07), 05-08.
- [2] Cicek G, Imamoglu O, Gullu A, Celik O, Ozcan O, Gullu E, Yamaner F. The effect of exercises on left ventricular systolic and diastolic heart function in sedentary women: Step-aerobic vs core exercises. *J Exerc Sci Fit*. 2017 .
- [3] Cooper, T. G., & Beevers, H. (1969). β oxidation in glyoxysomes from castor bean endosperm. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 244(13), 3514-3520.

AWARNESS ON JUNK FOOD CONSUMPTION PATTERN AMONGST TERTIARY LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Junk food is processed and prepared in an industrial fashion. Vitamins, minerals, fibre and amino acids are low or lacking in junk food but have high energy (calories). Nutrition is using each of energy and nutrition elements in the most economical way in sufficient amount necessary for growth, development and a healthy and efficient life, without losing their nutritional value and rendering them unhealthy. Type of nutrition of our age differs in comparison to the past. Nutritional habits of societies are considered to be depending on socio-economic, cultural, environmental, demographic and psychographic factors. Personal lifestyle affects consumption behaviours, namely, decisions on how to spend time, energy and money. Scarcity of time arose in connection with technological improvements, urbanization and women's participation in workforce, intensive work hours, single living and joining of women to social and economic life has increased the demand for junk food. Junk food consumption becomes the new and fast option for eating within brief noon hours in urban life. Eating out removes hunger and provides pleasure, entertainment, time saving, social activity and psychological assistance. Junk food nutrition which is considered an activity among children and youngsters and rapidly becomes a popular habit contains either insufficient or excessive nutrition elements. It consequently causes chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes, cardio-vascular diseases and cancer.

Keywords: Awareness, Junk Food, Consumption Pattern, Tertiary Level

Introduction

Junk food indicates food which is quickly prepared and served at outlets such as junk food restaurants. Healthy nutrition rich foods have been substituted by the new food named as junk food. Junk food is made and processed in an industrial fashion, i.e., with standard ingredients, consistent cooking and production methods. Vitamins, minerals, fiber and amino acids are low or lacking in junk food, but have high energy (calories). In the circumstance of the global economy, junk food is a universal phenomenon. The availability of junk food at minimum prices and marketing approaches adopted by manufacturers of such foods has elicited a progression of junk food at high rate. Junk food does not contain the nutrients which are required to sustain our body health. Therefore, these foods that have low nutritive value are considered injurious to health and may be named as junk food. Popularity of junk food in this era of growth has been attributed to speedy preparation and ease of finishing a food within no time. There is a rising trend among the tertiary students generation about junk food culture. Elder people are more fascinated about healthy foods as compared to tertiary student's generation. Junk food is a rising factor in the diet and since 1970s the rate of junk food use has grown intensely. Junk food is particularly common among tertiary level students, who often go to junk food stalls twice per week. Nutritional requirements in proper proportions, particularly in the younger age group assume a pivotal role in the overall development process. Medically it has been evidenced that the nutritional rate of junk food is less than the required amount and its consumption leads to several disorders. Also, the junk foods are key agents causing various disorders and diseases like obesity which is likely to cause heart diseases in the future. Tertiary level students are vastly exposed to harmful eating practices causing increased body weight.

Problems Associated With Junk Food

High Fat Content

Junk foods such as hamburgers, pizza, fried chic ken and chips usually loads of saturated fats, too much saturated fat in diet will cause people to put on weight and obese being overweight is a risk to the health of heart and causes other disease.

High Salt Content

Junk often have too much salt there is a lot of salt already in food such as bread, breakfast cereals and biscuits. So people are getting more salt than they need when they eat junk food too much salt is unhealthy for health.

High Sugar Content

Soft drinks, cordials, biscuits, cakes and lollies also have loads of sugar that's what makes them taste too good but too much sugar makes people fat, rots the teeth, is bad for the blood and may cause other disease. Junk food does have some of good things that the body needs for good health as the body needs some salt, fat and sugar for energy to burn while we p lay and work however too much fat, salt and sugar is bad for health. People tend to settle their meals by consuming junk food to save time. Researchers have shown that junk food might cause dyslexia, ADHD (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder) and may be autism.

Types of Junk Food

Various types of junk food is available in market out of which the most popular junk food is soft drink, pizza, hamburgers, potato chips, ice- creams, hot dog, pagoda, chowmins, French fries, cheese chilli, pav-bhaji etc. Junk food in north such as hamburgers and French- fries supplied by companies like McDonald's, KFC and Pizza Hut are often perceived as junk food, whereas similar meals supplied by mo re up - market outlets such Pizza Express or Nando's are often having the same or worse nutritional content Some food are considered ethnic or traditional are not generally considered junk food, such as gyro, pagoda, gyoza or chicharron, though all of these foods lave little nutritional value and are usually high in fat from being fried in oil. Similarly, breakfast cereals are often regarded as healthy but may have high levels of sugar, salt and fat.

Reasons of Popularity of Junk Food

The Time Factor: Junk food addiction is so high because of its simplicity. They are easy to prepare and are very tasty. Junk foods such as potato wafers and Cheetos do not even need cooking or heating. Peoples prefer to eat them while watching T V, they save themselves a lot of hassles and time when they are in a hurry eating pizzas and burgers as they are served at their door step hot and ready to eat.

The Taste Factor: If time constraint is one reason that pushes peoples to eating junk food, great taste also, to an extent influences them to opt for junk food. But junk foods get their taste owing to lavish usage of oils, salts and sugar. Global broadcaster BBC World and leading market research firm Synovate conducted a survey that showed Britons are more addicted to junk food than any other nation. Overall the survey showed that across the people have conflicting attitudes and behaviours about junk food. Once they caught in junk food addiction, they find it hard to think about the loss of nutrition due to junk food.

Junk Food Advertising: Foods prepared outside the home and restaurant foods have a great attraction for food buffs. An estimate tells that Frito Lays is selling a billion bags of Cheetos per year. Junk food advertising has a major role in this. There is also concern about the targeting of marketing to children because children are easy and potential target for junk food.

Shelf Life: Junk food has a long shelf life and may not require refrigeration for most products like chips and wafer.

Ease of Transportation: The transportation of junk food is easy due to its packaging as compare to the man made food. Ease of transportation and availability increase the popularity of junk food day by day.

Cost: The cost is less as compared to healthy food. Less cost is also a big reason of the popularity of junk food. It is easily accessible to all classes of population due to its low and attractive price range.

Reasons for Avoiding the Junk Food

Here is some junk food facts that help to understand the harmful effects associated with them. Some of them are long term while others are short terms effects. The fat contents have high cholesterol level. High calorie content with sugar can lead to obesity. Cholesterol and salt can increase blood pressure, stroke and heart disease in chain. Excessive salt can impaired the functioning of kidney too.

Lack of energy: This is known as short term adverse effect resulting from eating junk food as junk food don't provide the essential nutrients [like vitamins, protein and fibers]even though they can very much sufficing, peoples feel weakened.

Poor concentration: This is another result of junk food habit. These are t raced to effect in immediate and medium term periods when peoples have a sumptuous junk meal rich in oil they feel drowsy and fail to concentrate. Over sustained periods of junk food eating blood circulation drop due to fat accumulation, lack of vital oxygen, nutrients and protein particularly can stale their brain cells temporarily.

High cholesterol: Apart from forming plaques and constricting arteries cholesterol also affects liver where it is metabolized. High cholesterol due to junk food and diet strains liver damaging it finally. This is long term effect.

Heart diseases: Junk food diet is a major cause of heart diseases (Myocardial infarction) due to plaque formation in arteries which demands heart to put in extra effort to pump blood on the Downstream, on the upstream there is lack of returning blood to heart, this causes two damages to heart–heart fatigues due to continuous extra effort and it suffer in oxygen supply.

Low nutrition value: The nutritional value of junk food is about one on a scale of 1 to 10, which is the least. The nutritional value is lost in the process of making the junk food so synthetic Vitamins and minerals are added to compensate it, but they are not good compared to natural vitamins and minerals. Natural photochemical are not present in junk food which soaks up the free radicals to prevent disease.

Highly addictive: It is well known fact that fat and sugar are as addictive as heroin and cocaine, they stimulate the same receptors in the brain that make feel good due to increased dopamine level. Junk foods have a lot of hidden sugar and fat to make it addictive and also enhance the taste.

High chemical additives: Junk food have lots of chemical additives which are not useful to body, things are like artificial coloring and preservatives. MSG and tartrazine is in almost all type of junk food and all sorts of medical studies have revealed that MSG causes obesity and of other nasty things. All the techniques used to process the junk food –canning, dehydrating and freezing, virtually destroy the flavor of food so chemicals under the guise of ‘natural flavor’ have been added to enamel the flavor, while color additives are added to make food fresh. It might make the food look and taste better but it is harmful to our bodies.

Lack of oxygen supply: Junk food is rich in fat so accumulation of fat Can takes place in bronchioles so oxygen supply tends to reduced in body which can cause some respiratory disorders.

Conclusion

Eating habits have changed today due to technological improvements and changes in life condition, participation of tertiary level students. Scarcity of time has increased the demand for junk food. Good nutritional diet or balance diet is fundamental need for development and growth of human beings. Most of the student’s especially tertiary level students during their meal time have junk food and get habituated to the taste of the junk food. The junk food consists anything that is delicious, quick, fashionable and convenient. Though junk foods are tasty they have low nutritive value and high calories. Junk food habit counselling need to be regarding the significance of a balanced diet and harmful effects.

Reference

- [1] Sturm R, Powell LM, Chriqui JF, Chaloupka FJ. Soda taxes, soft drink consumption, and children’s body mass index. *Health Aff (Millwood)* 2010;29(5):1052–1058.
- [2] Story M, Nannery MS, Schwartz MB. Schools and obesity prevention: creating school environments and policies to promote healthy eating and physical activity. *Milbank Q.* 2009;87(1):71–100.
- [3] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2019). A Study On Self Efficacy Of Higher Secondary Students With Respect To Locality Of The Schools. *Think India Journal*, 22(10), 807-813.
- [4] Mani, M., & Prabu, M. M. (2019). Teachers self-efficacy scale: development and validation. *Review of Research*, 8(6), 1-8.
- [5] Mookkiah, M., & Kumar, S. (2021). YOGA BASED INTERVENTION STRATEGIES IN ACCELERATING SELF-EFFICACY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(4).
- [6] Taber DR, Chriqui JF, Perna FM, Powell LM, Chaloupka FJ. Weight status among adolescents in States that govern competitive food nutrition content. *Pediatrics.* 2012;130(3):437–444.
- [7] Kumar, S. (2020). Work Values of Secondary Grade Teachers based on certain selected variables. Mahalakshmi, N., Mahendraprabu, M., Mookkiah, M., & Kumar, S.(2020). Work Values of Secondary Grade Teachers based on certain selected variables. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, 12(3), 4910-4918.
- [8] Thorndike AN, Sonnenberg L, Riis J, Barraclough S, Levy DE. A 2-phase labeling and choice architecture intervention to improve healthy food and beverage choices. *Am J Public Health.* 2012;102(3):527–533.
- [9] Ervin RB, Ogden CL. Consumption of added sugars among US adults, 2005–2010. *NCHS Data Brief.* 2013;(122):1–8.
- [10] NIH, NHLBI Obesity Education Initiative Clinical Guidelines on the Identification, Evaluation, and Treatment of Overweight and Obesity in Adults. [Accessed March 1, 2015]. Available from: http://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/files/docs/guidelines/ob_gdlns.pdf

IMPACT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON MUSCULAR ENDURANCE OF COLLEGE WOMEN BASKETBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to find out the Impact of Yogic Practices on Muscular Endurance of College Women Basketball Players. For this purpose, Thirty Basketball Players were randomly selected from affiliated colleges of Alagappa University and their age ranged between 18 to 21 years. Subjects included in the study were not controlled with regard to their lifestyle, diet and habits which may have influenced their performance. The subjects' body type and the economic status were not taken into consideration. They were divided into two groups A and B with 15 Subjects in each group, group A was treated with Yogic Practices and group B was kept under control group. The subjects of group A underwent training for eight weeks with the duration of 45 minutes. The training was started at 6.30 a.m and it was given for four days per week for eight weeks. The pre-test and post-test on Muscular Endurance was measured. The data was statistically analyzed by using 't' ratio to find out the significant difference between the two groups. The finding of the study revealed that there was a slight significant improvement on Muscular Endurance for the experimental groups when compared to the control group.

Keywords: *Yogic Practices, Asana, Muscular Endurance*

Introduction

Basketball, extremely popular around the world, is a core game played by two teams of five Player each. The object is to put a ball through a hop, or basket and the score are points than the opposing team. Because of if continuous action and frequency scoring, Basketball is one of the most popular spectator as well as participant sports in the world. Ability of a Muscle group can contract over an extended time against Moderate Resistance. Training Muscular endurance will increase your Stamina as well; you will needless exertion in going from your job to playing with your Kids. Increasing Muscular Endurance will also limit Injuries sustained from Physical Exertion and from the Overuse of Active Muscles throughout the day.

Yoga has been practiced in India for two millennia. Stories and legends from ancient times testify to the existence of yoga, and to the practitioners and divinities associated with it. Indian literature is a store house of Knowledge about Yoga covering every conceivable level. Asana have a greater impact on the mind and the sense than the other Physical exercises with the result that Asana help to develop one's Physical and Mental powers to calm the mind and control the senses. Asana make possible not only physical and mental development but also intellectual and spiritual development. Asana require the least possible use of Physical energy.

Methodology

To achieve this purpose, Thirty College women Basketball players were randomly selected from affiliated colleges of Alagappa University. The subjects were ranged from 18 to 21 years. The subjects for this study were oriented and the purpose of the study explained. The testing procedures were explained to them in details, so that there was no ambiguity in their minds. The subjects were participated in this research with enthusiasm without any special motivational techniques. The subjects of the experimental groups received personalized attention and supervision of the trainer in relation to the Yogic Practices like Suryanamaskar, Padmasana, Vajrasana, YogaMudra, Dhanurasana, Bhujangasana, Paschimottanasana, Navasana, Tadasana, Shalabhasana, Pranayama (Nadi Suddhi, Bhastrika) and Meditation. The training was carried out in the multipurpose hall. The training was given forty five minutes in the morning hours at 6.30 a.m of 4 days a week for eight weeks. The subjects living condition and life-style were not taken into consideration for this study.

Table – 1 ‘t’ ratio of Muscular Endurance of Yogic Practices group and Control group

		Muscular Endurance			
		Yogic Practices Group	Control Group	Mean Differences	‘t’ ratio
Pre-test	Mean	14.40	14.60	0.02	3.83*
Post-test	Mean	18.47	14.73	3.74	0.13

*Significance at 0.05 level of confidence (required table Value is 2.15)

The mean score of Muscular Endurance between Yogic Practices group and Control group are 18.47 and 14.73 respectively. As the obtained ‘t’ ratio 3.83 is greater than required ‘t’ value 2.15 at 0.05 level of confidence at 14 degrees of freedom, there is slight significant improvement between Asana Practices group and Control group. The result shows that there was a significant difference between Yogic Practices group and Control group on the changes in Muscular Endurance after eight weeks of Training.

Fig – 1 The Pre and Post-test Mean Values of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group on Muscular Endurance

Conclusion

It was observed from the pre-test results, that there is no significant difference among Yogic Practices group and Control groups. While the post-test results of Yogic Practices group and Control group revealed that, there is a significant difference in the Yogic Practices group. The training program has influenced the Yogic Practices group where as there is no effect in the control group. The results of this study show that, after 8 weeks of practicing Yogic Practices, there was an improvement in Muscular Endurance.

References

- [1] Iyengar B.K.S(2001), Yoga – The path of Holistic Health, Dorling Kindersley Limited, Great Britain
- [2] Pramanik T, et.al. (2009),”Immediate effect of slow pace bhastrika paranayama on blood pressure and heart rate”, J Alert complement Med.2009 mar,1593:293-5.
- [3] Van L., et al., (1994), “The effects of Endurance Exercise with and without A Reduction of Energy Intake on Fat-Free Mass and the Composition of Fat-Free Mass in Obese Women”, European Journal of Clinical Nutrition., 48(6),pp.408-415.

TEACHING ENGLISH IN MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

Teaching English in higher education entails additional factors and considerations that exemplify the complexity of accounting for the diverse population in modern higher education institutions. In particular, the increasing flow of international students and the employment demands of functioning in multicultural contexts render helping students to develop a critical understating of intercultural relations an important aspect of English language teaching. With the increasing adoption of English as a medium of instruction and its use as a lingua franca in intercultural communication, it is important to structure English education in a way that accounts for intercultural relations both in and outside the university. In addition to the postmodern conceptualizations of interculturality that emphasize the fluidity of culture, language and identity intercultural relations are characterized by power imbalances. The English language classroom provides an obvious multicultural context for learning, and teachers need to help students understand and appreciate the differences and similarities among the various ethnic, religious and cultural groups. This paper aims to examine teachers' understanding of and attitudes towards multiculturalism, and in so doing, find out what are strategies used in promoting and enhancing successful multicultural interactions.

Keywords: *English Language Classroom, Multiculturalism, Teaching Strategies.*

Introduction

Multicultural education has one important message to give to all the students it serves, and it is that regardless of their differences in gender, social class, ethnicity, race, etc., they all deserve an equal opportunity to attain an equal education (Banks & Banks, 2001). To meet the needs of these diverse groups of students, adjustments in content and practice must be made in several areas, including reading, writing, and language (Cook & Lodge, 1996). When students see themselves in stories that are read in classrooms or can identify with the curriculum being taught, their voices become empowered and they establish a firm ground for their self-identity. Therefore, multicultural education motivates students to continue their academics with confidence and high self-esteem when they can identify themselves with the curriculum being taught. A handful of studies have shown that an educational experience filled with cultural curricula and bilingual instruction establishes empowerment for ELL students in different ways and therefore, has different effects on them socially, psychologically, and academically. Language is a vital means of transmitting culture and a common source of confusion, even among members of the same culture (Stavenhagen, 1990). Every language is part of a culture, and it serves and reflects cultural needs. Even so, there are areas in the world where societies share a very similar cultural orientation and yet speak languages that are not only mutually unintelligible but completely unrelated and structurally different. This is especially true when we have a class of students learning, and speaking English, all from varied cultural backgrounds.

Teachers' Understanding of and Attitudes Towards Multiculturalism

Teachers are the key factors in motivating, educating, and making a difference in the education of students irrespective of their gender, ethnicity, age, religion, language, or exceptionality. The majority of teachers usually, consciously or unconsciously, exhibit biases towards students in some manner, says Gollnick & Chinn (1991). There is then this possibility of a mismatch between teachers' teaching styles and the learning styles of culturally diverse students. A study conducted by Gay (1994), sees teachers as often perceiving their values, beliefs, and actions as the standard norms, and what they know and what they teach is governed by educational principles of teaching. Due to the lack of understanding of the ethnic, racial, social, and linguistic diversity of students, teachers can engage themselves consciously or unconsciously in practices that may not be suitable in the classroom. Due to the failure on the part of teachers to understand, accept, and appreciate who these students are, students may feel that the learning environment is alien and hostile toward them.

Issues in Teaching English in Multicultural Classrooms

- 1) Students belong to different lingual backgrounds.
- 2) No exposure towards the English language
- 3) Students feel shy.

- 4) They lack confidence.
- 5) There are no workshops for English teachers.
- 6) Lack of refresher courses.
- 7) Students make different mistakes in structure and pronunciation.
- 8) Cultural experiences of students differ.
- 9) Students have different learning styles.

Strategies for Incorporating Multicultural Education in the Classrooms

Foster a growth mindset in your classroom: A growth mindset helps the kids understand that the abilities they have can be improved with dedication and hard work and that they are just going through a stage of developing and improving. Foster inclusion: Inclusion applies to students of different races, ethnicities, classes, genders, and other groups. Design learning experiences around the cultural capital of the students: Teachers should recognize that the diverse experiences every student brings to the classroom can add richness to learning, and challenges students face outside the classroom do not always equate to deficits. Design learning challenges to include students working together: Bring students together through problem-based learning to solve real-world issues. Pairing students with different partners can help create an inclusive environment and foster empathy between classmates. Teaching effectively in a multicultural classroom requires culturally sensitive strategies and content to provide equal opportunities for academic success and individual growth of all students. Although multiculturalism is a common issue in the world, it is not much stressed in teacher training programmes.

Conclusion

Multicultural education requires time, resources, and professional development. Sometimes educators may feel like engaging in multicultural education is extra work. Every student is unique in their way, which includes unique characteristics. These qualities come with strengths and challenges such as deficiency in the English language. As a result, teachers must understand these attributes and respond with skill and sensitivity to help support each student to attain their full social, psychological and academic potential through the usage of multicultural education. Given this megatrend, every world citizen is responsible for learning and understanding the other culture through formal multicultural education in school or informal self-study through other different approaches. The English teacher, functioning as the cultural bridge, has the inescapable duty to transmit the best of the Eastern and Western cultures. The integration of multicultural education into English classes is the best combination. It offers them precious opportunities to proudly present their cultural heritage in front of their classmates who are unfamiliar with their traditions and cultures. The effects of multicultural education on ELL students showed signs of academic improvement due to their empowerment through personal narratives being taught in classrooms. It gives positive effects on their social acceptance and belongingness through the encouragement of their culture in classrooms. Overall, the implementation of multicultural education serves as a beneficial pedagogy for ELL students that affect them in positive manners academically, socially, and psychologically.

Reference

- [1] Allison, B.N. & Rehm, M.L. (2007). Teaching strategies for diverse learners in FCS classes. *Journal of family and consumer Sciences*, 99, 2. P. 8 Proquest Education Journals.
- [2] Banks, J. & McGee Banks, C. (2001). *Multicultural Education: Issues & Perspectives*. New York, N.Y.: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [3] Cook, L., & Lodge, H. (1996). *Voices in English classrooms: Honoring diversity and change (Classroom practices in teaching English; vol. 28)*. Urbana, Ill.: National Council of Teachers of English.
- [4] Davis, B.G. (1993). *Tools for teaching*. San Francisco. Jossey-Bass.
- [5] Gay, G. (1994). *A synthesis of scholarship in multicultural education*. Oak Brook Illinois, North Central Regional Laboratory.
- [6] Winch-Dummet, C. (2004). Teaching processes and practices from an Australian multicultural classroom; Two complimentary models. *International Education Journal*. Vol 4 No 4 pp 102-113.

A BRIEF PROFILE OF SIVAGANGA

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Abstract

During the Nayak period Small Sethu Nadu was otherwise called “Sivagangai Seemai”. It is one of the Marava kingdoms. Sasivarna Thevar formed Sivagangai palayam. He was the first ruler of Sivagangai Seemai. In Velu Nachiyar history, Marudu Brothers also played an important role in Sivagangai. There are a number of places of historical significance in and around Sivagangai. Sivaganga District was carved out from the composite Ramnad District on 6th July, 1984 and it started functioning from 15th March, 1985. Sethunadu was otherwise called Maravar Seemai. Regunatha Sethupathy alias Thirumalai Sethupathy was ruling Sethunadu during the period 1647-1672. Sasivarna Thevar ruined the forests areas furnished it into a city and named it as Sivagangai. Besides he constructed water ponds and build a palace nearby which the Raja Rajeswari Temple was constructed. The majestic palace was named as “Gowri Vilas” by Sasivarna Thevar.

Keywords: *Poligar, Palayam, Sethunadu, Sivagangai Seemai.*

Introduction

Sivagangai was known as Shevagungah in British period. It was one of the palayams during the Nayak period. In Velu Nachiyar history, Marudu Brothers also played an important role in Sivagangai. There are a number of places of historical significance in and around Sivagangai.

Sivaganga

Sivagangai was previously known as Sivaganga. It is an administrative district of Tamil Nadu located in Southern India. Sivaganga District was carved out from the composite Ramnad District on 6th July, 1984 and it started functioning from 15th March, 1985. The Sivagangai Seemai is historically an important territory. The Kingdom of Ramnathapuram comprised of the territories of the present Ramnathapuram, Sivagangai and Pudukottai. Sivagangai region was ruled by brave and valour leaders like, Sasivarna Thevar, Raja Muthu Vaduganatha Peria Oodaya Thevar, Rani Velu Nachiyar and Marudhu Brothers. Velu Nachiyar re-captured Sivagangai Samasthan with the help of Hyder Ali and was crowned as the Queen of the Sivagangai Seemai. Velu Nachiyar was the first queen who raised the revolt against the English Empire and fought for Indian freedom. Queen Velu Nachiyar remained as a symbol of bravery for many freedom fighters. She became a role model for women.

Early Formation of Sivagangai

Sethunadu was otherwise called Maravar Seemai. Regunatha Sethupathy alias Thirumalai Sethupathy was ruling Sethunadu during the period 1647-1672 and he appointed his relatives who belonged to the “Uthamanur” to organise the tax collection from the western side of his country. He constructed a castle near Choolapuram to his relative who could look after all duties from the castle. That castle was called Nalukottai Palayam. The people who administered were called Nalukottai Palayakkars. Sasivarna Thevar was the son of Periya Udaiya Thevar and his first wife who was a descent of these Palayakkars. Thiruvudaya Thevar alias Vijaya Regunatha Sethupathy (1710-1725) solemnized his daughter with Sasivarna Thevar. He made Periya Udaiya Thevar sworn in as the commander of thousand knights and Sasivarna Thevar was sworn in as the Governor of Velli Kurichi area. Thanda Thevar alias Andaeswarar Regunatha Sethupathy became as the king of Sethunadu by extorting it after killing the king. As a result Kattaya Thevar alias Muthu Vijaya Regunatha Sethupathy who was responsible for Government property which made him refuse to the Tanjore king. Bavani Sahar again confined the portfoil and so Sasivarna Thevar also made him refuse to Tanjore king with the support of Kattaya Thevar and Sasivarna Thevar fought with Bavani Sahar and captured Sethunadu. In 1728, Sethu Nadu was divided into two parts – three fifth (3/5) of it was Big Sethu Nadu and the other two-fifth (2/5) was Small Sethu Nadu. Big Sethu Nadu was called as Periya Marravar Nadu. It was also referred to as Ramanathapuram Seemai. Kattaya Thevar alias Vijaya Regunatha Sethu was sworn in as the King of these areas. Small Sethu Nadu was otherwise called Sivaganga Seemai. Sasivarna Thevar ruined the forests areas furnished it into a city and named it as Sivagangai. Besides he constructed water ponds and build a palace nearby which the Raja Rajeswari Temple was constructed. The majestic palace was named as “Gowri Vilas” by Sasivarna Thevar. Sasivarna Thevar had the pride in the forming of Sivagangai and the first king of Sivagangai Seemai. Muthu Vadukanathar who married Velu Nachiyar was the son of Sasivarna Thevar and

his second wife Boothakka Nachiyar. After the death of Sasivarna Thevar. His young son became the king of Sivagangai Seemai.

Administrative Setup

The Sivaganga district has two revenue divisions namely Sivaganga and Devakottai. It has six taluks. They are Thirupathur, Karaikudi, Devakottai, Manamadurai, Ilayankudi and Sivaganga. The taluks consists of 522 revenue villages of which Sivaganga has more than 100 revenue villages. A Block is a development unit for a district and it consists of about one lakh population or approximately 20,000 households. The Sivaganga district has 12 blocks and 445 village Panchayats.

Physical Features

The geographical extent of the district is 4,189 sq.km, accounting for 3.22 per cent of the geographical area of Tamil Nadu State. Out of the total geographical area, agricultural land comes around 27.6 per cent, forest area constitute 5.2 per cent, and other fallow lands constitute 33.35 per cent, which is very significant, and cultivable waste is around 4 per cent. The red sandy soil is found in almost all the parts of the district. The district receives an average rainfall of 700 mm in a year. The bulk of the rainfall is received during the North-East monsoon between October and December. Hot and dry weather prevails for about nine months in a year and characterized by frequently hit droughts. The North-East Monsoon helps the agriculturist to show self-sufficiency in the production of cereals, particularly paddy, ragi and corn.

Industry

The Sivaganga district is not only an agriculture area, but it also an important to industrial oriented region. There are about 26 spinning and weaving mills in the district. Tamil Nadu Chemical Industries at Karaikudi, Central Electro Chemical Research Institute at Karaikudi, Sakti Sugar Factory at Padamathur and Madras Motors at Singampunari are the major industries in the district. Graphite is the only major mineral that is being excavated by Messer's Tamil Nadu Mineral Limited (TAMIN). The district is also noted for its handloom industry and manufacturing of stainless steel at Karaikudi. Manamadurai centre, bricks, brick tiles and pot making centers at Manamadurai and Thiruppuvanam areas and coir manufacturing industries (Handmade) are providing employment to the rural and urban women in the Singampunari and S.Pudur blocks. The growth of the Small Scale Industrial (SSI) units provide greater employment opportunities, for the rural and semi-urban folks.

Transport and Communication

The means of transportation are roadways and railways. National highways and State highways pass through Sivagangai for a length of 54.5 km and 2.02 km respectively. The length of corporation and municipality road is 257 km. The Panchayat union and town Panchayat union roads are for a length of 2100 km and 1930 km respectively. A railway line passes through the district for a 155.52 km meter gauge and there are 17 railway stations in the district. The public communication includes post and telegraph and telephones.

Location and Geographical Area

Sivagangai district is having a geographical area of 4189 sq. km, in the Southern part of Tamil Nadu. It lies between 9 43' and 10 47' of the Northern latitude and 77 47' and 78 49' of Eastern longitude. The district is located in the southern part of Tamil Nadu and surrounded by Ramanathapuram district in East and South, Virudhunagar and Madurai Districts in West, Tiruchirappalli and Pudukkottai districts in the north. Normal rainfall in the district is 872.8 MM.

Soil

Soil is one of the most valuable natural resources, without soil life is impossible on earth. Red Soil and Black Soil are the two kinds of soil found in Sivagangai. Black Soil is predominantly available in this district. Some part of Sivaganga district has red soil also.

Climate

The district experiences a very dry and hot climate with low degree of humidity. Normally, the temperature varies from 22°C to 39°C. There are no perennial rivers in the district. The river Vaigai is the only major one which enters the district near Thiruppuvanam and flows through Sivaganga block. The other seasonal rivers and minor streams flowing through the district are Sarugani, Bambar, Kottagudi, Manimuthar, Uppar, Uppargundam and Thenar in Thirupathur block.

Language

The main language spoken in Sivaganga is Tamil. Although Tamil is the official language of the State, and is the common language of communication across Tamil Nadu, there are many dialects and slangs. In Sivaganga, Tamil is influenced by the dialects spoken by the people of Chettinad, who tend to speak more words drawn from traditional Tamil.

Art, Architecture and Culture

The art, culture and architecture of Sivaganga is predominantly characterized by Chettinad. Chettinad is famous for its traditional jewelry, silver ware, Kandanghi Sarees (hand woven), Kidarams (big vessels), brass vessels, palmyra leaf basket, clay and wooden toys (especially Chettiyar and Aachi) and decorative Kolam (art work). Chettinad is also known for many clan temples, Ayyanar shrines and Mariyamman Temples. One of the master pieces of Chettinad architecture can be seen in the Rajas palace at Kanadukathan.

Tourism Development

Tourism is an activity that is emblematic of the 21st century. The Sivaganga district has many tourism attractions, such as Chettinad, Kalayarkoil, Devakottai, Pillaiyarpatti, Kunrakudi, Vettangudi Bird Sanctuary, Thirupattur, Thirukoshtiyur, Natarasankottai, Kollangudi, Sivaganga, Thayamangalam, Madappuram, Piranmalai, Idaikattur Church, Thirupachethi, and Vairavanpatti. The Sivaganga district administration has taken various initiatives to promote tourism in the district, with main focus on 'Chettinadu'.

Demographic Features

According to census 2011, the population of Sivaganga stood at 13.39 lakh, which was 1.85 lakh greater than the population according to the Census 2001 (11.54 lakh). The decennial growth rate of population in 2011 was 16.07 per cent. When compared to 2001, the decennial growth rate has increased just above three fold. This increased growth in population in Sivaganga can be attributed to better standard of living and improvement in health services. The density of population per sq.km; increased to 320.46 in 2011 from 277.16 in 2001. This shows that people were moving towards urban area or urbanisation was picking up a pace.

Agriculture

Agriculture is the backbone of the society. The district's principal crops are rice, millets and other cereals, pulses, sugarcane, groundnut, ginger and cotton, in which, rice was cultivated in nearly 70 per cent of the area followed by sugarcane in 5.93 per cent of the area. The main sources of irrigation are tanks, tube wells and other wells out of which, nearly 65 per cent of the irrigation is covered by tanks followed by other wells (33.68 per cent) and tube wells (2.2 per cent). One important aspect to note that the area covered by Prosopis Julifora (Veli Karuvai) is the highest among all the districts in Tamil Nadu.

Literacy and Education

The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at the primary level for both boys and girls was quite high at 102.58 per cent and 102.29 per cent respectively in the year 2013-14. The total literacy rate of Sivaganga Taluk is 79.06%. The male literacy rate is 78.11% and the female literacy rate is 63.57% in Sivaganga Taluk.

Conclusion

This articles aims to know the history of Sivaganga. Its give a major role in Velu Nachiyar and the Marudu Brothers in Sivagangai. The purpose is to make some impression on the present generations among the Sivagangai and create awareness among them about formation history of Sivaganga. Because Velu Nachiyar was the first women who raised her voice against British administration. Sivaganga history is an important history in Tamil Nadu.

References

- [1] Josias Du Pre and Council 13 July, 1772, Military Consultations, Vol.42, p.608.
- [2] District Human Development Report, Sivaganga, 2007, p.2.
- [3] Brief Industrial Profile Sivagangai (2015-16), p.4.
- [4] Kamaal, S.M., Seermiu Sivagangai Seemai, Pasumpon District Art, Literature & Historical Research Centre, Sivagangai, 1997,p.
- [5] Jeevabharathi, K., Velu Nachiyar, Kumaran Publications, Chennai, 2001,pp. 40-41.

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Multicultural education is a progressive approach in transforming education by exposing the shortcomings and failures of discriminatory practices in education. Multicultural societies need a holistic approach because the existence of cultural diversity requires a system that can appreciate existing cultures. Besides the society, Multicultural education is built by developing synergistic knowledge, which creates new perceptions in the face of knowledge development. Through creative and innovative strategies, multicultural education is being optimized in the environment of higher education institutions. With multicultural education, students will get a global perspective on facing various problems in the industrial revolution era. Holistic education focuses on developing universal human values and nurtures the understanding and respect crucial to living harmoniously in society. Multicultural education challenges and rejects racism and other forms of discrimination in schools and communities. When all these for mentioned dimensions are applied, the multicultural education represents a way of rethinking school reform because it responds to many problematic factors leading to school underachievement. Thus, the outcome based education is need of the hour which meets the whole demands of the today's learners. The outcome based education worry about the skill and outcome of the learners than the information monker. The conference highlights the importance of using multicultural values in life and enriching multicultural artifacts to foster a multicultural spirit integrated with holistic education and outcome based education.

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